

Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (12)

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Inder Taneja published two papers on Zenodo (combining results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
18-01-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ²⁸
03-02-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20000 to 30000 ²⁹

Authors published thirteen papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title	Date	Title
24-12-2018	Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴	14-12-2018	Simplifications (01) ¹³
02-01-2019	Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵	02-08-2019	Simplifications (02) ³⁹
28-01-2019	Fill the Gaps (03) ²⁵		
06-02-2019	Fill the Gaps (04) ³⁰		
07-02-2019	Fill the Gaps (05) ³¹		
19-07-2019	Fill the Gaps (06) ³⁶		
23-07-2019	Fill the Gaps (07) ³⁷		
30-07-2019	Fill the Gaps (08) ³⁸		
08-08-2019	Fill the Gaps (09) ⁴⁰		
14-08-2019	Fill the Gaps (10) ⁴¹		
14-08-2019	Fill the Gaps (11) ⁴²		

Historic Overview

Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases ¹⁶

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 11 through 16):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (completing the base 11 up to 16 series):

Date	Title
09-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX) ²³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (extending the base 16 series):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFF) ²⁴

Authors published two papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 17 through 62):

Date	Title
23-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to #####) ²⁶
02-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 62 (0000 up to #####) ²⁷

Authors published four papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 3 through 9):

Date	Title
13-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 9 (0000 up to 8888) ³²
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 8 (0000 up to 7777) ³³
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 7 (0000 up to 6666) ³⁴
18-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 3 up to 9 ³⁵

Examples - Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 10 crazy sequential representations (increasing and decreasing):

2671₁₀	48₁₀
$1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*89_{10}$	$9_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$

Examples - Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 11 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

5491₁₀	4142₁₁	378₁₀	314₁₁
$-1_{11}/2_{11}*(3_{11}-4_{11}+5_{11})^{6_{11}}+7_{11}*89A$		$A9_{11}^{8_{11}-7_{11}}*6_{11}/(-5_{11}+4_{11}+3_{11})+21_{11}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*1077_{10}$		$119_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 12 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

6853₁₀	3B71₁₂	419₁₀	2AB₁₂
$-1_{12}/2_{12}*(3_{12}-4_{12}+5_{12})^{6_{12}}+7_{12}*89A_{12}+B_{12}$		$B_{12}+A9_{12}^{8_{12}-7_{12}}*6_{12}/(-5_{12}+4_{12}+3_{12})+21_{12}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*1270_{10}+11_{10}$		$11_{10}+129_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 13 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

8460₁₀	3B0A₁₃	605₁₀	377₁₃
$-1_{13}/2_{13}*(3_{13}-4_{13}+5_{13})^{6_{13}}+7_{13}*89A_{13}+BC_{13}$		$CB_{13}+A9_{13}^{8_{13}-7_{13}}*6_{13}/(-5_{13}+4_{13}+3_{13})+21_{13}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*1479_{10}+155_{10}$		$167_{10}+139_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 14 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

12217₁₀	4649₁₄	302₁₀	178₁₄
$-1_{14}/2_{14}*(3_{14}-4_{14}+5_{14})^{6_{14}}+7_{14}*89A_{14}+BCD_{14}$		$D_{14}-CB_{14}+A9_{14}^{8_{14}-7_{14}}*6_{14}/(-5_{14}+4_{14}+3_{14})+21_{14}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*1704_{10}+2337_{10}$		$13_{10}-179_{10}+149_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 15 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

14221₁₀	4331₁₅	530₁₀	255₁₅
$-1_{15}/2_{15}*(3_{15}-4_{15}+5_{15})^{6_{15}}+7_{15}*89A_{15}+BCD_{15}-E_{15}$		$ED_{15}-CB_{15}+A9_{15}^{8_{15}-7_{15}}*6_{15}/(-5_{15}+4_{15}+3_{15})+21_{15}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*1945_{10}+2668_{10}-14_{10}$		$223_{10}-191_{10}+159_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 16 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

16148₁₀	3F14₁₆	4402₁₀	1132₁₆
$-1_{16}/2_{16}*(3_{16}-4_{16}+5_{16})^{6_{16}}+7_{16}*89A_{16}+BCD_{16}-EF_{16}$		$FED_{16}-CB_{16}+A9_{16}^{8_{16}-7_{16}}*6_{16}/(-5_{16}+4_{16}+3_{16})+21_{16}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^{6_{10}}+7_{10}*2202_{10}+3021_{10}-239_{10}$		$4077_{10}-203_{10}+169_{10}^{8_{10}-7_{10}}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Definition - Base 10 Crazy Sequential Representation

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
 Evaluation results in an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
 Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 + - * / ^ ()

Digits 1 up to 9 occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$

Representations with **negation** of **segments in parentheses** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$(1+2-3)*(45*-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7*-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45/-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7/-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45^-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$-(1+2)+3*(45^(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^(6^5)+4)*(-(3-2)+1)$
$-(1-2+234*(6-(7+8-9)))$	$-((9-(8+7-6))*543-2+1)$

Representations without negation of segments in parentheses are referred to as “genuine”.

Note

Previously, authors used ‘CSR’ to refer to crazy sequential representations that evaluate to natural numbers (as originally introduced by Inder Taneja) and ‘NCSR’ to refer to crazy sequential representations that evaluate to negative integers (as introduced by ourselves). Authors always avoided ‘PCSR’ as this might introduce ambiguity (pseudo vs. positive CSR).

From this point forward, authors will use the following:

- CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any integer
- +CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any positive integer
- CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any negative integer

Note

As far we’re aware, our previous work ^{6-8,12-15,25,30,31,36-42} contains 16 invalid expressions.

Five expressions which do not contain each digit in appropriate order:

Integer	Invalid	Valid Alternative
474	$9*8+7*(54+3)+2+1$	$98+7-6+54+321$
475	$9+8+5*(7+6)*(4+3)+2+1$	$98+76-5*4+321$
512	$98+7*(54+3+2)+1$	$9*8+765-4-321$
10102	$1+(2+56*(3*4))*(7+8)-9$	$1+(2+3*4*56)*(7+8)-9$
-10102	$-(1+(2+56*(3*4))*(7+8)-9)$	$-1-(2+3*4*56)*(7+8)+9$

Eleven expressions which do not evaluate to an integer value:

Integer	Invalid		Valid Alternative
-1124589382	$9^{-8-7-65^4*3*21}$	$\approx$	-1124589381.999999...
-410062320	$-9*((8+7)^6-5)*4+3^{-21}$	$\approx$	-410062319.999999...
-75499812	$-9*(8^7+65)*4+3^{-21}$	$\approx$	-75499811.999999...
43046792	$9^8+76-5+43^{-21}$	$\approx$	43046792.000000...
43046797	$9^8+76+5/43^{21}$	$\approx$	43046797.000000...
43047046	$9^8+7^{-65+4+321}$	$\approx$	43047046.000000...
43047486	$9^8+765-43^{-21}$	$\approx$	43047485.999999...
43164370	$9^8+7^6-5/43^{21}$	$\approx$	43164369.999999...
124571609	$(1-2^{-34+5*6^7})*89$	$\approx$	124571608.999999...
301327047	9^8*7+65^{-4321}	$\approx$	301327047.000000...
1124589368	$9^{-8-7+65^4*3*21}$	$\approx$	1124589368.000000...

Aim

Attempt to ‘fill the gaps’ in our previous work ^{6-8,12-15,25,30,31,36-42} by identifying...

- increasing genuine CSR for integers without any increasing genuine CSR.
- decreasing genuine CSR for integers without any decreasing genuine CSR.

Results

Authors identified 36826 previously unknown genuine CSR, see supplements.

	Increasing +CSR	Decreasing +CSR	Increasing -CSR	Decreasing -CSR
Genuine	5069	13593	5051	13113

Overview

Currently, within the -2147483647 up to 2147483647 range, increasing CSR are available for 1859649 integers, and decreasing CSR are available for 2658523 integers:

	Increasing +CSR	Decreasing +CSR	Increasing -CSR	Decreasing -CSR
Genuine	927913	1331292	924557	1304851
Pseudo*	2018	179	5161	22201
Total	929931	1331471	929718	1327052

*pseudo CSR in case no genuine CSR available

Note

Authors consider CSR to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial.

Authors do not guaranty:

- Published CSR are the shortest in existence.
- Published CSR are in their simplest form.
- Unavailable CSR do not exists.

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Supplement 1

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
30085	$1+2+(3^4*5-67)*89$	85431	$(1+(2^3-4^5/(6/7))*8)^*-9$
30354	$-12+3^4*5*(67+8)-9$	85611	$(1+(2+(3-4^5)/(6/7))*8)^*-9$
31676	$-1+(2+3^4*56)*7-89$	85647	$(1+(2+3-4^5/(6/7))*8)^*-9$
36218	$(-1-2)*(3^4-(5^6*7+8)/9)$	85665	$(1-(2+3-4^5/(6/7))*8)^*9$
38334	$12+3^4*(5+6*78)+9$	85917	$(1+(2-(3-4^5)/(6/7))*8)^*9$
40039	$-1*2+(3^4+56*78)*9$	86367	$(-1+(2+3+4^5/(6/7))*8)^*9$
40043	$1*2+(3^4+56*78)*9$	86421	$(1+(2+(3+4^5)/(6/7))*8)^*9$
40124	$1*2+(3^4*56-78)*9$	86439	$(-1+(2*3+4^5/(6/7))*8)^*9$
40197	$12-3^4*(5-67)*8+9$	86601	$(1+(2^3+4^5/(6/7))*8)^*9$
40947	$-12+(3^4*56+7+8)*9$	87597	$(-1+(2/3^4-4-5)*(6+7*8))^*9$
41195	$-12+((3^4-5)*6+7)*89$	87944	$12+(3^4-5)*(6+7)*89$
42005	$-1-2+(3^4*5+67)*89$	91417	$(1-2/3^4-4*5)*(6-7*(8+9))$
42270	$-12-3^4*(5-67*8+9)$	91842	$-12-3^4*(5-67*(8+9))$
43842	$12+3^4*(5+67*8)+9$	93131	$-1+2*(3^4*(567+8)-9)$
45213	$1-2*(3^4-5*67)*89$	93133	$1+2*(3^4*(567+8)-9)$
47302	$-1*2+3^4*(567+8+9)$	93169	$1+2*(3^4*(567+8)+9)$
49548	$12+(3^4+5)*6*(7+89)$	94134	$12+3^4*(5+(6+7)*89)$
51288	$-12+(3^4-5)*(67+8)*9$	94923	$(1+2*(3^4*5*(6+7)+8))^*9$
51918	$-12+((3^4+5)*67+8)*9$	95486	$-1/(2+3+4)+5^6*(7-8/9)$
53043	$-12+3^4*5*(6*7+89)$	98158	$(12+(3^4+5)*67)*(8+9)$
53050	$-12-(3^4+5)*(6-7*89)$	99132	$-12+3^4*(5+67)*(8+9)$
54106	$12+(3^4+5)*(6+7*89)$	99514	$12+(3^4+5)*(6+7)*89$
54412	$12*(3^4*56-(7+8)/9)$	100698	$(-1+(2*3)^4/5)*6*(7*8+9)$
54452	$12*(3^4*56+(7+8)/9)$	101125	$(-1+2/3^4-4*5)*(6+7*(8+9))$
54476	$1/(2/((3^4-5^6)^*-7))+8*9$	104361	$(1-2/3^4-4*5)*(6-(7+8)*9)$
55068	$-12+3^4*(5+(67+8)*9)$	105494	$1/2+(3/4*(5^6-7)+8)*9$
55716	$-12-(3^4+5)*(6-78)*9$	105808	$(1-(2-3^4*(5+6))*7)*(8+9)$
58038	$-12+(3^4+5)*(67+8)*9$	105958	$(1-2^3/3^4)*(5^6*7-8+9)$
58062	$12+(3^4+5)*(67+8)*9$	106218	$(1+2)*(3^4*5+6^7/8+9)$
58251	$12+3^4*(5+6*7*(8+9))$	107940	$(-1+((2*3)^4-5)/6)*7*8*9$
60159	$-12*(3^4*(5-67)+8)-9$	108511	$(-1+2*(3^4-5)*6*7*(8+9))$
60163	$-1+2*(3^4*5-67)*89$	109007	$-1-2*(3^4*(5-678)+9)$
60177	$-12*(3^4*(5-67)+8)+9$	109009	$1-2*(3^4*(5-678)+9)$
60843	$12-3^4*(5-(6+78)*9)$	111065	$(1+2^3*(4+(5^6-7)*8))/9$
61295	$(1+(2/3^4-4-5)*6)*(7*8+9)$	112113	$(-1+2*(3^4*(5+6)*7-8))^*9$
61653	$12+3^4*(5+(6+78)*9)$	112794	$(1+2^3/3^4)*(5^6*7-8+9)$
62044	$12*3*(-4+(5^6-78)/9)$	113599	$(1+(2-3^4*5)*6)*(7*-8+9)$
62867	$-1-(2-3^4*5)*(67+89)$	113693	$(1-(2-3^4*5)*6)*(7*8-9)$
62956	$12*3*(4+(5^6+78)/9)$	114727	$(-1+(2+3^4*5)*6)*(7*8-9)$
63826	$-1*2+3^4*(5-6+789)$	114821	$(1+(2+3^4*5)*6)*(7*8-9)$
63841	$-1/2-3^4*(5/6-789)$	115195	$1+(2*(3^4-5)-6)*789$
63842	$1/2-3^4*(5/6-789)$	115765	$(1-2/3^4-4*(5+6))*(7-8*9)$
63977	$1/2+3^4*(5/6+789)$	115884	$12*(3^4+5*6)*(78+9)$
64802	$1*2+3^4*(5+6+789)$	116645	$(-1-2/3)/(4/(5-6^7-8-9))$
66027	$12+3^4*(5+6*(7+8)*9)$	121519	$(1+(2*3+4)*(5^6*7-8))/9$
67375	$1+((2^3)^4+5*678)*9$	125379	$(-1+2*3^4*(5*6+7*8))^*9$
69231	$12*((3^4+5)*67+8)-9$	125397	$(1+2*3^4*(5*6+7*8))^*9$
69477	$-12+3^4*(5+6)*78-9$	126562	$-1/2-3^4*5^6/(7-8-9)$
70188	$12*(3^4*(5+67)+8+9)$	126563	$1/2-3^4*5^6/(7-8-9)$
71901	$(1+2*(3^4*(5*6*(5*6+7)*8-9))$	127287	$(-1+2*(3^4*(5+6)-7)*8)*9$
72590	$1*2+(3^4+5+6)*789$	129455	$(1+2/3^4-4*(5+6*7))*(8+9)$
73050	$-12-3^4*(5+6)*(7-89)$	133983	$(1+(2-3^4*(5*6-7))*8)^*-9$
74497	$(1+(2/3^4-4-5)*6)*(7+8*9)$	134001	$(1-(2-3^4*(5*6-7))*8)^*9$
75912	$12*(3^4*(5+6)*7+89)$	135430	$12+(3^4+5^6*78)/9$
76855	$(-1+2/3^4-4*5)*((6+7)*8-9)$	138513	$-1+23^4-(5^6+78)*9$
76981	$-12+(3^4*56-7)*(8+9)$	139182	$-12-(3^4-5^6+78)*9$
77045	$(1+2/3^4-4*5)*((6+7)*8-9)$	139854	$12-3^4+(5^6-78)*9$
77505	$-12+3^4*(5+6)*78+9$	140255	$-1-234+(5^6-7-8)*9$
78664	$-12+(3^4*(5+6)-7)*89$	140257	$1-234+(5^6-7-8)*9$
78688	$12+(3^4*(5+6)-7)*89$	140857	$(1+2/3^4-4*(5+6))*(7+8*9)$
78884	$-12*(3^4-5/6)*(7-89)$	140894	$-1-234+(5^6+7*8)*9$
80083	$1+2*(3^4+56*78)*9$	140993	$-1+234+(5^6+7+8)*9$
80838	$-12*3^4*(5/6*7-89)$	140995	$1+234+(5^6+7+8)*9$
82086	$-12+3/4*(5^6*7+89)$	141396	$1+2*34+(5^6+78)*9$
83051	$-1+2*(3^4*56+78)*9$	142068	$12+(3^4+5^6+78)*9$
83053	$1+2*(3^4*56+78)*9$	149715	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5+6)*7*8+9)$
83596	$-12*(3-4*(5^6+7*8)/9)$	157235	$(1-(2-3^4*5)*6)*(7*8+9)$
83694	$12*(3^4-5/6)*(78+9)$	158665	$(-1+(2+3^4*5)*6)*(7*8+9)$
83707	$(-1+2*3^4*(5+6))*(7*8-9)$	164739	$(-12+3^4*(5*6-7))*89$
83801	$(1+2/3^4-4*(5+6))*(7*8-9)$	169512	$(1-2*(3-4^5/6))*7*8*9$
85348	$-1-2+(3^4+56)*7*89$	171987	$(1-2*(3-4^5/(6/7/8)))^*9$
85386	$12-3^4*(5-67)*(8+9)$	172077	$(-1+2*(3+4^5/(6/7/8)))^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
172095	$(1+2*(3+4^5/(6/7/8)))^*9$	250938	$(1+2)^*3^4*(5^6/(7+8)-9)$
174303	$(1+(2-3^4*5^6+7)^*8)^*-9$	257376	$(1+(2-3/4^5)/6)^*7^*8^*-9$
174321	$(1-(2-3^4*5^6+7)^*8)^*9$	260199	$(-1+(2+(3^4+5)^*6^*7)^*8)^*9$
174552	$(-1+2*(3+4^5/6))^*7^*8^*9$	260217	$(1+(2+(3^4+5)^*6^*7)^*8)^*9$
175599	$(-1+(2+3^4*5^6+7)^*8)^*9$	261063	$(-1+(2+(3^4+5)^*6)^*7^*8)^*9$
176402	$1/2*((3+4)^5/(6/7)-8)^*9$	261081	$(1+(2+(3^4+5)^*6)^*7^*8)^*9$
176546	$1/2*((3+4)^5/(6/7)+8)^*9$	261689	$(1+(2^3)^4*(567+8))/9$
178167	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5-6^(7-8)))^*9$	262293	$(12+3^4*5)^*(6+7^*8^9)$
178185	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5-6^(7-8)))^*9$	262452	$12-3^4*5*(6-7^*8)^*9$
178993	$(1-2/3^4-4^5*(6+7))^*(-8-9)$	264543	$(1-2/3^4-4^5)^*(6^*7^*-8+9)$
179027	$(1+2/3^4-4^5*(6+7))^*(8+9)$	265197	$(1+2^*3^4*5)^*(6^*7^*8-9)$
192839	$(-1+(2+3^4*5)^*6)^*(7+8^*9)$	270330	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(7+8-9)$
192997	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^*6)^*(7+8^*9)$	270342	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(7+8-9)$
194423	$(1+2*(3^4-5^6*7)^*8)/-9$	273195	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5+6/7^*8^*9)^*9$
194443	$(1-2*(3+4-5^6*7^*8))/9$	273267	$(-12+3^4*5*(67+8))^*9$
198659	$-12/(3+4)+5^6/7^*8^9$	273427	$(1+2/3/4)^*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$
200943	$(1+(2-(3^4*5-6)^*7)^*8)^*-9$	273448	$(1+2/3/4)^*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$
200961	$(1-(2-(3^4*5-6)^*7)^*8)^*9$	274239	$(-1+(2+3^4*5*(5+6^*7))^*8)^*9$
201231	$(-1+(2+(3^4*5-6)^*7)^*8)^*9$	274257	$(1+(2+3^4*(5+6^*7))^*8)^*9$
206292	$12*(3^4-4^5*6^7-8^9)$	281109	$(1+2)^*((3/4)^5*6^7-8^9)$
207111	$(-12+3^4*5)^*(67^*8-9)$	281391	$(1+2)^*((3/4)^5*6^7-8^9)$
207279	$(-1+(2+(3^4*5+6)^*7)^*8)^*9$	281445	$(1+2)^*((3/4)^5*6^7+8^9)$
208428	$12*(3^4-4^5*6^7+8^9)$	282491	$-1-2*(3^4-(5^6+7^*8)^*9)$
212075	$(1+2/3^4-4^5*(5+6)^*7)^*(8+9)$	282493	$1-2*(3^4-(5^6+7^*8)^*9)$
213180	$-12+3^4*5^6*(7^*8-9)$	282586	$1^*2*(-34+(5^6+7^*8)^*9)$
213204	$12+3^4*5^6*(7^*8-9)$	282667	$-1+2*(3+4+(5^6+7^*8)^*9)$
213423	$-12+3^4*5^6*(67^*8-9)$	282723	$1+2*(3+4+(5^6+7^*8)^*9)$
213447	$12+3^4*5^6*(67^*8-9)$	286706	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6+7-8+9)$
214185	$(-12+3^4*5)^*(67^*8+9)$	286734	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6+7-8+9)$
214947	$(-12+3^4*5^6*(67-8))^*9$	287725	$(1+(2-3^4*5)^*6^*7)^*(-8-9)$
215043	$-12+3^4*5^6*(67-8)^*9$	288414	$(-12+(3^4*5+6)^*7^*8)^*9$
215067	$12+3^4*5^6*(67-8)^*9$	288915	$(1+(2-3^4*5^6)^*7)^*(-8-9)$
215163	$(12+3^4*5^6*(67-8))^*9$	288949	$(1-(2-3^4*5^6)^*7)^*(8+9)$
215919	$(-1+(2+3^4*(5^6+7))^*8)^*9$	289391	$(-1+(2+3^4*5^6)^*7)^*(8+9)$
217437	$-1-2*((3^4-5^6)^*7+8^9)$	289425	$(1+(2+3^4*5^6)^*7)^*(8+9)$
217793	$-1-2*((3^4-5^6)^*7-8^9)$	290581	$(-1+(2+3^4*5)^*6^*7)^*(8+9)$
217795	$1-2*((3^4-5^6)^*7-8^9)$	290615	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^*6^*7)^*(8+9)$
218859	$-1-2*(34-5^6*7-8^9)$	291708	$(12+3^4*(5^6+7+8))^*9$
218995	$-1+2*(34+5^6*7+8^9)$	294507	$(-1+2^*3^4*(5^6*7-8))^*9$
218996	$1^*2*(34+5^6*7+8^9)$	294525	$(1+2^*3^4*(5^6*7-8))^*9$
219089	$-1+2*(3^4+5^6*7+8^9)$	306027	$(-1+2*(3^4*5^6*7-8))^*9$
219091	$1+2*(3^4+5^6*7+8^9)$	306333	$(1+2*(3^4*5^6*7+8))^*9$
219705	$-1+2*((3^4+5^6)^*7-8^9)$	307185	$(1-(2^3)^4*5)^*(6/(7-8)-9)$
219707	$1+2*((3^4+5^6)^*7-8^9)$	307215	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6^*(7+8)+9)$
220061	$-1+2*((3^4+5^6)^*7+8^9)$	310023	$(-1+((2^3)^4+5^6*7)^*8)^*9$
220063	$1+2*((3^4+5^6)^*7+8^9)$	310041	$(1+((2^3)^4+5^6*7)^*8)^*9$
220713	$-12+3^4*5^6*(67^*8+9)$	310841	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+67^*8))/9$
224883	$(1-(2-3^4*5)^*(6+7^*8))^*9$	313145	$(-1+2^*3^4*(5^6+7)/8-9)$
224900	$1/(2+3)^*(4+(5^6-7)^*8^*9)$	314765	$-1+(2^3^4-56+7)/8^*9$
227097	$(-1+(2+3^4*5)^*(6+7^*8))^*9$	315835	$(-1+2/3^4-4^5*5^6)^*(7^*8+9)$
227115	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^*(6+7^*8))^*9$	315965	$(1+2/(3^4-4/5)^*6)^*(7^*8+9)$
228373	$(-1+2/3^4-4^5*6)^*(7^*8-9)$	316043	$(-1+2^*3^4*(5^6+7)/8+9)$
228467	$(1+2/(3^4-4/5)^*6)^*(7^*8-9)$	317035	$(1+2^*3^4*(5^6+7)/8-9)$
229671	$(1+(2-(3^4-5)^*6^*7)^*8)^*-9$	317736	$12*(3^4*(5^6*7-8)-9)$
229977	$(1+(2+(3^4-5)^*6^*7)^*8)^*9$	319098	$(-1+(2^3)^4/5)^*6*(7^*8+9)$
230823	$(-1+(2+(3^4-5)^*6)^*7^*8)^*9$	319423	$(1-(2^3)^4/(5/6))^*(7-8^*9)$
232245	$(1-2^*(3^4))^*(5-6/(7/8/9))^*9$	319553	$(1+(2^3)^4/(5/6))^*(7^*8+9)$
236366	$12*((3+4)^5/(6/7)+8^9)$	319969	$(1+2^*3^4*(5^6+7)/8+9)$
238491	$(12+3^4*(5^6*7-8))^*9$	320220	$(12+(3^4-5)^*6^*7^*8)^*9$
240561	$(-1+2/3^4-4^5*(5+6)^*(7+8))^*9$	320241	$(12^*3)^4-5^6*(7^*8+9)$
240579	$(1+2/3^4-4^5*(5+6)^*(7+8))^*9$	321456	$-12+(3^4+5)^*6^*7^*8^9$
242481	$(12-3^4*5)^*(6-7^*8^9)$	324756	$12^*3^4*(5^6*7-8/9)$
243051	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4^5*6^7-8))/9$	325980	$(-12+(3^4*5^6-7)^*8)^*9$
244233	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+(6+7)/8))^*9$	326196	$(12+(3^4*5^6-7)^*8)^*9$
245750	$(1-2^*(3+4+5)^*6)^*(7-8-9)$	326373	$(-1-2)*((3^4-5^6)^*7+8+9)$
245770	$(1+2^*(3+4+5)^*6)^*(-7+8+9)$	326421	$(-1-2)*((3^4-5^6)^*7-8+9)$
246105	$(1-2*(3-4-5^6*7)/8)^*9$	326427	$(-1-2)*((3^4-5^6)^*7+8-9)$
246267	$(-1+2*(3^4+5^6*7)/8)^*9$	326475	$(-1-2)*((3^4-5^6)^*7-8-9)$
246285	$(1+2*(3^4+5^6*7)/8)^*9$	327204	$(12+(3^4*5^6+7)^*8)^*9$
247197	$(-12+3^4*5)^*(6+7^*8^9)$	327666	$(1+2)*(-3^4+5^6*7-8^*9)$
247851	$(1-2/3^4-4^5*(6^*7-8))^*-9$	327756	$(1+2)*(-34+5^6*7-8^9)$
247869	$(1+2^*3^4*5*(6^*7-8))^*9$	327789	$(1-(2-3^4*5^6)^*(7+8))^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
327831	$(1+2)^*(-3^4+5^6*7-8-9)$	402882	$(1-2/(3^4-4/5))^*(6-7*8*9)$
328407	$1+2+3*(4+5^6*7+89)$	403878	$(1+2*3^4*5)^*(-6+7*8*9)$
328419	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6*7+8+9)$	404387	$1-23*(4-(5^6+7)/8*9)$
328494	$(1+2)^*(3+5^6*7+89)$	405859	$-1+234*(5^6-7-8)/9$
328584	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6*7+8*9)$	405861	$1+234*(5^6-7-8)/9$
329610	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5^6)*7-8*9)$	406225	$1+234*(5^6+7-8)/9$
329661	$(-1+(2+3^4*5)*6*(7+8))^*9$	406235	$-1-2-3*(4-5^6*78/9)$
329679	$(1+(2+3^4*5)*6*(7+8))^*9$	406236	$1*-2-3*(4-5^6*78/9)$
329775	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5^6)*7-8-9)$	406237	$1-2-3*(4-5^6*78/9)$
329829	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5^6)*7-8+9)$	406275	$-1+234*(5^6-7+8)/9$
329877	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5^6)*7+8+9)$	406639	$-1+234*(5^6+7+8)/9$
330042	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5^6)*7+8*9)$	407492	$-1-(2-3^4*(567-8))^*9$
333321	$(1+2)^*(3^4/5^6-6-7)*8/9$	407494	$1-(2-3^4*(567-8))^*9$
337635	$(12-3^4*(5-6*78))^*9$	407528	$-1+(2+3^4*(567-8))^*9$
342552	$(1+2/(3/(4^5-6)))^*7*8*9$	407530	$1+(2+3^4*(567-8))^*9$
344709	$(-12+3^4*(5+6*78))^*9$	408701	$-1+(2+(3^4+5)*6)*789$
344925	$(12+3^4*(5+6*78))^*9$	408703	$1+(2+(3^4+5)*6)*789$
348903	$(-1+2*(3^4*5*6-7)*8)*9$	412590	$(-1+2*3^4*5)^*(6+7*8*9)$
348921	$(1+2*(3^4*5*6-7)*8)*9$	413252	$-1-(2-3^4*567+8)*9$
350919	$(-1+2*(3^4*5*6+7)*8)*9$	413288	$-1+(2+3^4*567-8)*9$
350937	$(1+2*(3^4*5*6+7)*8)*9$	413290	$1+(2+3^4*567-8)*9$
351373	$(12^3(3-4+5)-67)^*(8+9)$	413396	$-1-(2-3^4*567-8)*9$
352794	$(-1+2*((3+4)^5/(6/7)-8))^*9$	413398	$1-(2-3^4*567-8)*9$
353100	$(1+2*((3+4)^5/(6/7)+8))^*9$	413434	$1+(2+3^4*567+8)*9$
353651	$(12^3(3-4+5)+67)^*(8+9)$	413610	$(1+2/(3^4-4/5))^*(6+7*8*9)$
355752	$12*3^4*(5*(67+8)-9)$	414693	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4*5/6^8-7*8-9)$
358137	$1+((2^3)^4-5-67)*89$	414747	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4*5/6^8-7*8+9)$
358938	$1+((2^3)^4-56-7)*89$	414756	$(-12+(3^4+5)*67*8)*9$
360184	$1+((2^3)^4-56+7)*89$	414852	$-12+(3^4+5)*67*8*9$
360440	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(7-8+9)$	414972	$(12+(3^4+5)*67*8)*9$
361361	$-1+(2+(3^4-5)*6)*789$	418608	$12*(3^4-5)^*(6*78-9)$
361363	$1+(2+(3^4-5)*6)*789$	419156	$-1-(2-3^4*(567+8))^*9$
361476	$(12+3^4*(5-67)*8)*-9$	419158	$1-(2-3^4*(567+8))^*9$
361692	$(12-3^4*(5-67)*8)*9$	419192	$-1+(2+3^4*(567+8))^*9$
362124	$(-12+(3^4+5)*6*78)*9$	419194	$1+(2+3^4*(567+8))^*9$
366612	$-12+(3^4-5)*67*8*9$	419667	$(1+2)^*(-34+(5^6-78))^*9$
366636	$12+(3^4-5)*67*8*9$	419765	$1+23^4+(5^6-78)*9$
366732	$(12+(3^4-5)*67*8)*9$	419782	$-1+2+3*(4+(5^6-78)*9)$
367390	$-1-(2-3^4*567)*8-9$	419783	$1*2+3*(4+(5^6-78)*9)$
367442	$1+(2+3^4*567)*8+9$	420327	$(1+2)^*(3^3-4+(5^6-7*8))^*9$
368622	$(1-(2^3)^4*5)^*(6-7-8-9)$	420375	$1^2*3*(4+(5^6-7*8))^*9$
368658	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(-6+7+8+9)$	421167	$-1+23^4+(5^6+78)*9$
370063	$1+((2^3)^4-5+67)*89$	421169	$1+23^4+(5^6+78)*9$
372861	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-5^6+7)*8+9)$	423351	$(1+2)^*(3^3-4+(5^6+7*8))^*9$
372915	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-5^6+7)*8-9)$	423375	$(1-2)*3*(4-(5^6+7*8))^*9$
374562	$(1+2)^*(-3^4+(5^6+7)*8-9)$	423399	$1^2*3*(4+(5^6+7*8))^*9$
375438	$(1+2)^*(3^4+(5^6+7)*8+9)$	423423	$(1+2)^*(3^4+(5^6+7*8))^*9$
376803	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5^6-7)*8+9)$	423879	$(1+2)^*(-34+(5^6+78))^*9$
377085	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5^6+7)*8-9)$	423957	$-12-3*(4-(5^6+78))^*9$
377139	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5^6+7)*8+9)$	424083	$(1+2)^*(34+(5^6+78))^*9$
377199	$(1+(2-3^4*5)^*(6+7)*8)*-9$	426708	$12*((3^4-5)*6*78-9)$
377217	$(1-(2-3^4*5)^*(6+7)*8)*9$	426924	$12*((3^4-5)*6*78+9)$
378927	$(1+(2-3^4*5*(6+7))^*8)*-9$	435416	$-12^3+4*(5^6*7-89)$
378945	$(1-(2-3^4*5*(6+7))^*8)*9$	436128	$-12^3+4*(5^6*7+89)$
379233	$(1+(2+3^4*5*(6+7))^*8)*9$	437108	$-12*3+4*(5^6*7-89)$
380943	$(-1+(2+3^4*5)^*(6+7)*8)*9$	437120	$-1-23+4*(5^6*7-89)$
380961	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^*(6+7)*8)*9$	437121	$-1*23+4*(5^6*7-89)$
381111	$12*(3^4*5*6*7+8)-9$	437122	$1-23+4*(5^6*7-89)$
381129	$12*(3^4*5*6*7+8)+9$	437129	$-12-3+4*(5^6*7-89)$
381996	$12*3^4*(5*6*7-8+9)$	437166	$-1+23+4*(5^6*7-89)$
382812	$1/2*((3+4)*5^6*7+8-9)$	437168	$1+23+4*(5^6*7-89)$
384019	$(1+2/(3^4-4/5))^*6*(7+8*9)$	437180	$12*3+4*(5^6*7-89)$
387111	$12-3^4*(5-67*8)*9$	437188	$-1-23+4*(5^6*7-8*9)$
388692	$12*(3^4*(56*7+8)-9)$	437197	$-12-3+4*(5^6*7-8*9)$
390327	$-12-3^4*(5-67*8)*9$	437209	$1^2*-3+4*(5^6*7-8*9)$
390351	$12-3^4*(5-67*8)*9$	437791	$(-1+2)*3+4*(5^6*7+8*9)$
391137	$-12+3^4*(5+67*8)*9$	437820	$-12*3+4*(5^6*7+89)$
394281	$(-12+3^4*(5+67*8))^*9$	437832	$-1-23+4*(5^6*7+89)$
394377	$-12+3^4*(5+67*8)*9$	437834	$1-23+4*(5^6*7+89)$
394401	$12+3^4*(5+67*8)*9$	437871	$12+3+4*(5^6*7+89)$
394497	$(12+3^4*(5+67*8))^*9$	437878	$-1+23+4*(5^6*7+89)$
398366	$(12*3)^4+5^6*(7-89)$	437879	$1*23+4*(5^6*7+89)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
437892	$12^*3+4^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$	497909	$1^*2+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+678)^*9$
438872	$12^{\wedge}3+4^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$	497910	$1+2+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+678)^*9$
439584	$12^{\wedge}3+4^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$	497924	$-1+(2+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+678))^*9$
448911	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6)^*7)^*8)^*-9$	501423	$(1+2/(3/(4^*5)))^*(6^{\wedge}7/8-9)$
448929	$(1-(2-3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6)^*7)^*8)^*9$	504999	$(-1+(2^*3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^*7^*8)^*9$
449199	$(-1+(2+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6)^*7)^*8)^*9$	505017	$(1+(2^*3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^*7^*8)^*9$
449217	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6)^*7)^*8)^*9$	507772	$-1/2^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7-8^*9))$
450063	$(-1+(2+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6)^*7)^*8)^*9$	507853	$1/2^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7^*8+9))$
450550	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*(5+6))^*(7-8-9)$	508272	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4)^*5^{\wedge}6^*7)/(-8-9)$
450570	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*(5+6))^*(-7+8+9)$	511975	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6^*7-8-9)$
451971	$(-1+2^*3^{\wedge}4^*5^*(6+7^*8))^*9$	512025	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6^*7-8-9)$
451989	$(1+2/(3^{\wedge}-4/5)^*(6+7^*8))^*9$	512244	$12^*3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6^*(78+9))$
453011	$1-(2-(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*67)^*89$	512995	$-1+(2+(3^{\wedge}4+5)^*67)^*89$
453365	$-1+(2+(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*67)^*89$	512997	$1+(2+(3^{\wedge}4+5)^*67)^*89$
453367	$1+(2+(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*67)^*89$	519954	$(-1+23/4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$
455129	$-1+234^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)/8-9)$	523557	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}-4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7/8+9)$
455131	$1+234^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)/8-9)$	524753	$-1-(2-(3^{\wedge}4+5)^*678)^*9$
457075	$(1+234)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)/8-9)$	526149	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}-4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7/8-9)$
457226	$-1+234^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)/8-9$	526203	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}-4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7/8+9)$
457228	$1+234^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)/8-9$	538623	$-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4+5)/6^*789$
457244	$-1+234^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)/8+9$	538625	$1+2^{\wedge}(3+4+5)/6^*789$
457246	$1+234^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)/8+9$	539772	$-12+3^{\wedge}4^*56^*7^*(8+9)$
457379	$(-1+234)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)/8+9)$	539796	$12+3^{\wedge}4^*56^*7^*(8+9)$
459341	$-1+234^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)/8+9)$	541655	$-12+(3+4^*5^{\wedge}6^*78)/9$
459343	$1+234^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)/8+9)$	541679	$12+(3+4^*5^{\wedge}6^*78)/9$
459639	$(-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^*7^*8)^*9$	549163	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5^*678-9)$
459657	$(1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^*7^*8)^*9$	549197	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5^*678+9)$
461305	$(1+234)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)/8+9)$	549199	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5^*678+9)$
461499	$(12+3^{\wedge}4^*5^*67)^*(8+9)$	554025	$(-12+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6)^*7)^*89$
463735	$1-(2-(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*678)^*9$	555081	$-12+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6)^*7^*89$
463769	$-1+(2+(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*678)^*9$	555105	$12+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6)^*7^*89$
463771	$1+(2+(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*678)^*9$	556161	$(12+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6)^*7)^*89$
466494	$-1+(23^{\wedge}4+56)^*(7+8)/9$	558883	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5-6^{\wedge}7+89)$
466496	$1+(23^{\wedge}4+56)^*(7+8)/9$	558885	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5-6^{\wedge}7+89)$
467517	$(-12+3^{\wedge}4^*5^*(6+7))^*89$	559239	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5-6^{\wedge}7-89)$
468835	$-1+2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8)+9)$	559241	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5-6^{\wedge}7-89)$
468837	$1+2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8)+9)$	560503	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6^{\wedge}7-89)$
469653	$(12+3^{\wedge}4^*5^*(6+7))^*89$	560505	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6^{\wedge}7-89)$
470569	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^{\wedge}5/(6/7/8)-9)$	560859	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6^{\wedge}7+89)$
470623	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^{\wedge}5/(6/7/8)+9)$	560861	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6^{\wedge}7+89)$
474759	$(-1+(2^*3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^*7^*8)^*9$	561420	$12^{\wedge}3+4^*(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9$
474777	$(1+(2^*3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^*7^*8)^*9$	563179	$-1^*23+(4^*5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9$
474795	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)/8-9)$	563180	$1-23+(4^*5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9$
474849	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)/8+9)$	563224	$-1+23+(4^*5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9$
482004	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5-67)^*8+9)$	563225	$1^*23+(4^*5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9$
482220	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5-67)^*8-9)$	563580	$-12^{\wedge}3+4^*(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9$
482589	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4^*(5-6^*7^*8))^*-9$	564930	$12^{\wedge}3+(4^*5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9$
482607	$(1-2/(3^{\wedge}-4/(5-6^*7^*8)))^*9$	573648	$12^*(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6+7^*89)$
486109	$(1-(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7^*8))^*/9$	583412	$12^*(3+4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+8)/9)$
490598	$-1-(2+3^{\wedge}4^*(5-678))^*9$	583671	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*(5/6+7+8))^*9$
490600	$1-(2+3^{\wedge}4^*(5-678))^*9$	583689	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*(5/6+7+8))^*9$
490614	$-1-2-3^{\wedge}4^*(5-678)^*9$	592918	$(-1+(23^{\wedge}4+5)/6/7)^*89$
490615	$1^*-2-3^{\wedge}4^*(5-678)^*9$	601491	$(12^*3)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6^*(78-9)$
490616	$1-2-3^{\wedge}4^*(5-678)^*9$	612348	$-12+3^{\wedge}4^*56^*(7+8)^*9$
490618	$1^{\wedge}2-3^{\wedge}4^*(5-678)^*9$	612372	$12+3^{\wedge}4^*56^*(7+8)^*9$
490619	$1^*2-3^{\wedge}4^*(5-678)^*9$	614370	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6+7+8+9)$
490620	$1+2-3^{\wedge}4^*(5-678)^*9$	614430	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6+7+8+9)$
490634	$-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4^*(5-678))^*9$	616248	$12^*3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6+7^*89)$
490636	$1+(2-3^{\wedge}4^*(5-678))^*9$	619786	$(1+2/3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+8-9)$
491508	$12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*56+7+8)^*9$	619888	$(1+(2/3+4))^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+8+9)$
492132	$1/-2^*(3+(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7+8)^*9)$	622557	$(-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5-6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$
492135	$1/2^*(3-(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7+8)^*9)$	622575	$(1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5-6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$
492160	$1/-2-(3-4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7/8)^*9$	625374	$(-12+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6)^*78)^*9$
492161	$1/2-(3-4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7/8)^*9$	625590	$(12+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6)^*78)^*9$
492204	$1/-2^*(3+(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7-8)^*9)$	629417	$-1+23/4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+89)$
492207	$1/2^*(3-(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7-8)^*9)$	629419	$1+23/4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+89)$
492214	$-1/2+(3+4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7/8)^*9$	629676	$(-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5-6^{\wedge}7)/8)^*9$
492215	$1/2+(3+4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7/8)^*9$	630036	$(1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5+6^{\wedge}7)/8)^*9$
492240	$1/2^*(-3+(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7+8)^*9)$	637137	$(-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$
492243	$1/2^*(3+(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7+8)^*9)$	637155	$(1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$
497906	$1-2+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+678)^*9$	640642	$1/2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89))$
497908	$1^{\wedge}2+3^{\wedge}4^*(5+678)^*9$	645000	$(1+2/3)^*(4^{\wedge}5^*6^*7-8)^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
650469	$(-1+(2^3)^4/5)^*(6+789)$	841020	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5+6^7+8-9)$
652059	$(1+(2^3)^4/5)^*(6+789)$	841026	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5+6^7+8+9)$
655854	$12^*(3+4*(5^6*7/8-9))$	841239	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5+6^7+8*9)$
656097	$1+2^*(3*(4+5^6*7)-89)$	849920	$(-1-2/3)/(4^4-5/(6-7*8^9))$
656222	$(1-2^3)^*(4-5^6*(7+8-9))$	854163	$-1-2/3^*(4+5^6*(7-89))$
656278	$(1+2^3)^*(4+5^6*(7+8-9))$	870816	$(-1+2^3*4^5*6)^*(7+89)$
657721	$(1+2^3*4^5)^{(-6+7-8+9)}$	871008	$(1+2^3*4^5*6)^*(7+89)$
660299	$(1+23^4*5^6*7)/89$	874283	$1-2^*(3-4*(5^6*7-89))$
666404	$12^*(3+4*(5^6-7)^*8/9)$	874293	$-1+2^*(3+4*(5^6*7-89))$
687624	$(-1+2^3/4^4-5/6)^*7*8^9$	874573	$(1+2^3)^*(4+(5^6-7)^*8-9)$
688632	$(1+2^3/4^4-5/6)^*7*8^9$	874643	$(1-2^3)^*(4-(5^6-7)^*8-9)$
694984	$1/2^*(-34+(5^6-7)^*89)$	874699	$(1+2^3)^*(4+(5^6-7)^*8+9)$
695018	$1/2^*(34+(5^6-7)^*89)$	875301	$(1-2^3)^*(4-(5^6+7)^*8+9)$
695607	$1/2^*(-34+(5^6+7)^*89)$	875357	$(1+2^3)^*(4+(5^6+7)^*8-9)$
695641	$1/2^*(34+(5^6+7)^*89)$	875427	$(1-2^3)^*(4-(5^6+7)^*8-9)$
699507	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-5^6)^*(7+8)-9)$	875707	$1-2^*(3-4*(5^6*7+89))$
699634	$-1+(2+3)^*(4+(5^6-78)^*9)$	875717	$-1+2^*(3+4*(5^6*7+89))$
706654	$-1+(2+3)^*(4+(5^6+78)^*9)$	880597	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6^7-8+9)$
706743	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5^6)^*(7+8)-9)$	880683	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6^7-8+9)$
707965	$(1+2/3+4)^*((5^6-7)^*8-9)$	889287	$(-1+2^3*4)^*(5^6+7)/8/9$
708067	$(1+2/3+4)^*((5^6-7)^*8+9)$	905199	$(-1+2^3(3+4+5)^*(6+7))^*(8+9)$
711504	$12/3^4-4*(5^6+78^9)$	905233	$(1+2^3(3+4+5)^*(6+7))^*(8+9)$
718779	$(-1+2^*(3^4-5)^*6)^*789$	906287	$(-1+2^*(3^4-5)^*6)^*789$
720617	$(1+2^3-3)^*(4+5+6+7^8/9)$	906465	$(1+2^*(3^4-5)^*6)^*789$
729093	$-1+2^*(3+4^5(5-6+7)^*89)$	923916	$12^*(3^4*5^6-7)^*(8+9)$
729165	$(1+2/3)^*(4/(5^6-6/7)+8-9)$	924868	$1/(2/((3^4-5^6)^*7))^*(-8-9)$
729195	$(1+2/3)^*(4/(5^6-6/7)+8+9)$	926772	$12^*(3^4*5^6+7)^*(8+9)$
733617	$(1+2)^*3^4*(-5+6^7*8^9)$	927513	$(1+2^*(3^4-5)^*6)^*789$
734813	$-1+2^*(3^4*5^6*7+8-9)$	929647	$1/2^*(-3^4+5^6*7^*(8+9))$
734851	$1+2^*(3^4*5^6*7+8+9)$	929720	$1/2^*(-3+(4+5^6*7)^*(8+9))$
736047	$(1+2)^*3^4*(5+6^7*8^9)$	929723	$1/2^*(3+(4+5^6*7)^*(8+9))$
743822	$(1-2^3*4^5*6)^*(7-89)$	936102	$(-1+(2^3*4-5)^*6)^*789$
745281	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5-6^7*8/9)$	976552	$-1/2^*(3^4-5^6(-6+7+8)+9)$
747711	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5+6^7*8/9)$	976573	$1/2^*(3^4+5^6(-6+7+8)+9)$
749933	$1-2^*(3^4-5^6*(7+8+9))$	976765	$1/2^*(3^4*5+(6+7-8)^9)$
749983	$1/2^*(-34+5^6*(7+89))$	979449	$-12+(3+4)^*(5^6-78)^*9$
750017	$1/2^*(34+5^6*(7+89))$	979473	$12+(3+4)^*(5^6-78)^*9$
750067	$-1+2^*(34+5^6*(7+8+9))$	980819	$(1-2^3)^*(4-(5^6-7^*8)^*9)$
753870	$-1+2^3*(4^5(5-6+7)^*8+9)$	980875	$(-1+2^3)^*(4+(5^6-7^*8)^*9)$
764990	$-12+(3+4)^*(5^6*7-89)$	981243	$(1-2^3*4^5*(5-6^78))^*9$
765014	$12+(3+4)^*(5^6*7-89)$	983402	$(1-2^3)^*(4-(5^6-7-8)^*9)$
765093	$(1-2^3)^*(4-5^6*7+8^9)$	983458	$(1+2^3)^*(4+(5^6-7-8)^*9)$
765149	$(-1+2^3)^*(4+5^6*7-8^9)$	983661	$-12+((3+4)^*5^6-78)^*9$
765478	$(1-2^3)^*(4-5^6*7+8+9)$	983685	$12+((3+4)^*5^6-78)^*9$
765772	$(1+2^3)^*(4+5^6*7+8+9)$	984068	$-1-234+(5^6*7-8)^*9$
766101	$(1-2^3)^*(4-5^6*7-8^9)$	984070	$1-234+(5^6*7-8)^*9$
766157	$(-1+2^3)^*(4+5^6*7+8^9)$	984680	$-1+234+(5^6*7+8)^*9$
766236	$-12+(3+4)^*(5^6*7+89)$	984682	$1+234+(5^6*7+8)^*9$
766260	$12+(3+4)^*(5^6*7+89)$	985065	$-12+((3+4)^*5^6+78)^*9$
777783	$(-1+2^*(3+4/5^6-6^7)^*8)/9$	985089	$12+((3+4)^*5^6+78)^*9$
796275	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	985292	$(1-2^3)^*(4-(5^6+7+8)^*9)$
796542	$12+3^*(4+(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	985348	$(1+2^3)^*(4+(5^6+7+8)^*9)$
796761	$(1+2)^*(3^4+(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	985443	$12^*(3/4*5^6*7+89)$
796989	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-(5^6+7)^*(8+9))$	987875	$(1-2^3)^*(4-(5^6+7^*8)^*9)$
797268	$(1+2)^*(3^4+(5^6+7)^*(8+9))$	987931	$(-1+2^3)^*(4+(5^6+7^*8)^*9)$
797475	$(1+2)^*(3^4+(5^6+7)^*(8+9))$	989277	$-12+(3+4)^*(5^6+78)^*9$
798283	$-1-23^4+5^6*(78-9)$	989301	$12+(3+4)^*(5^6+78)^*9$
798284	$-1^*23^4+5^6*(78-9)$	991185	$(1+2/3+4)^*5^*(6^7/8-9)$
798285	$1-23^4+5^6*(78-9)$	991695	$(1+(2/3+4))^*(5^*(6^7/8+9))$
806251	$(1+2^*(3^4*5^6-7))^*89$	995732	$(-1+(2^3*4+5)^*6)^*789$
808565	$(-1+2^*(3^4*5^6+7))^*89$	995805	$(-1+2^3*4^5*(5+6^78))^*9$
808743	$(1+2^*(3^4*5^6+7))^*89$	995823	$(1+2^3*4^5*(5+6^78))^*9$
809190	$1^2/(3^4(-4-5)/(6^7-8/9))$	995910	$(1+(2^3*4+5)^*6)^*789$
812475	$-1-2^3*(4-5^6*78/9)$	1043448	$12+3/4^*(5^6+7)^*89$
816372	$12^*(3^4*5^6*(7+8)-9)$	1069065	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5^6+7-8))^*9$
816588	$12^*(3^4*5^6*(7+8)+9)$	1071213	$-12^3*4+5^6*(78-9)$
838377	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5-6^7+8^9)$	1072524	$-12-(3^4-5^6)^*(78-9)$
838542	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5-6^7+8+9)$	1072548	$12-(3^4-5^6)^*(78-9)$
838590	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5-6^7+8-9)$	1073655	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5^6-7/8))^*9$
838596	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5-6^7+8-9)$	1073673	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5^6-7/8))^*9$
838644	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5-6^7+8-9)$	1076393	$-12^3-4+5^6*(78-9)$
840972	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5+6^7+8-9)$	1076401	$-12^3+4+5^6*(78-9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1077153	$-12 \cdot 3^4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1225737	$(1 + (2+3^4 \cdot 5^6)) \cdot 7^8 \cdot 9$
1077693	$-12^3 / 4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1228838	$(1 + (2+3)^4) \cdot ((5^6 + 7) / 8 + 9)$
1077981	$-12 \cdot 3^4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1230759	$(-1 + (2+3^4 \cdot 5^6)) \cdot 6^7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9$
1078023	$(-1-2) \cdot 3^4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1230777	$(1 + (2+3^4 \cdot 5^6)) \cdot 6^7 \cdot 8 \cdot 9$
1078032	$-1 \cdot 23^4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1239521	$(1 + 2/3 \cdot (4 - 5^6 \cdot 7)) \cdot (-8-9)$
1078034	$1 - 23^4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1239555	$(1 - 2/3 \cdot (4 - 5^6 \cdot 7)) \cdot (8+9)$
1078091	$1^2 \cdot -34 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1244007	$(1 + (2 - 3^4 - 4 \cdot 5^6 / 6^7 - 7)) \cdot 8 \cdot 9$
1078108	$-1/2 \cdot 34 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1244025	$(1 - (2 - 3^4 - 4 \cdot 5^6 / 6^7 - 7)) \cdot 8 \cdot 9$
1078142	$1/2 \cdot 34 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1244295	$(-1 + (2 + 3^4 - 4 \cdot 5^6 / 6^7 - 7)) \cdot 8 \cdot 9$
1078159	$1^2 \cdot 34 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1244313	$(1 + (2 + 3^4 - 4 \cdot 5^6 / 6^7 - 7)) \cdot 8 \cdot 9$
1078213	$(-1+23) \cdot 4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1253359	$(-1 + (2^3)^4 \cdot (5+6+7)) \cdot (8+9)$
1078216	$-1 \cdot 23^4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1253393	$(1 + (2^3)^4 \cdot (5+6+7)) \cdot (8+9)$
1078227	$(1+2) \cdot 34 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1257201	$12 \cdot (3/4 \cdot 5^6 - 78) \cdot 9$
1078557	$12^3 / 4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1258566	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 78 - 9)$
1079097	$12 \cdot 3^4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1258590	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 78 - 9)$
1079533	$-1 \cdot 23^4 + 5^6 \cdot (78+9)$	1259286	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 78) - 9$
1079534	$-1 \cdot 23^4 + 5^6 \cdot (78+9)$	1259304	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 78) + 9$
1079535	$1 - 23^4 + 5^6 \cdot (78+9)$	1259328	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 78) + 9$
1079849	$12^3 - 4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1260024	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 78 + 9)$
1079857	$12^3 + 4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1260048	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 78 + 9)$
1081320	$(-1 + (2^3)^4 \cdot (5+6)) \cdot (7+8+9)$	1264957	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 7) - 89$
1083702	$-12 + (3^4 + 5^6) \cdot (78-9)$	1264981	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 7) - 89$
1083726	$12 + (3^4 + 5^6) \cdot (78-9)$	1265135	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 7) + 89$
1085037	$12^3 \cdot 4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1265159	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 7) + 89$
1085387	$(-1 + (2^3)^4 \cdot 5^6) \cdot (6+7 \cdot 8-9)$	1266091	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7) - 89$
1085493	$(1 + (2^3)^4 \cdot 5^6) \cdot (6+7 \cdot 8-9)$	1266115	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7) - 89$
1093778	$(1 + 2^3) \cdot (4 - 5^6 \cdot (7-8-9))$	1266269	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7) + 89$
1102883	$(-1 + (23^4 - 5) \cdot 67) / (8+9)$	1266293	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7) + 89$
1119379	$1 - 2^3 \cdot (3 - 4 \cdot (5^6 - 78) \cdot 9)$	1271202	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 78 - 9)$
1120000	$(1 + 2^3) / (4 \cdot 5)^6 \cdot (6+7-8-9)$	1271226	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 78 - 9)$
1122389	$-1 \cdot (234 - (5^6 - 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	1271922	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 78) - 9$
1122391	$1 \cdot (234 - (5^6 - 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	1271940	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 78) + 9$
1123397	$-1 \cdot (234 - (5^6 + 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	1271964	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 78) + 9$
1123399	$1 \cdot (234 - (5^6 + 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	1272660	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 78 + 9)$
1124972	$(1 + 2^3) \cdot (-4 + 5^6 / (7/8/9))$	1272684	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 78 + 9)$
1125028	$(1 + 2^3) \cdot (4 + 5^6 / (7/8/9))$	1272700	$-12 \cdot (3 - 4^5 / (6/7)) \cdot 89$
1126601	$-1 + (234 + (5^6 - 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	1274596	$-12 + (3^4 - 5^6) \cdot (7-89)$
1126603	$1 + (234 + (5^6 - 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	1274620	$12 + (3^4 - 5^6) \cdot (7-89)$
1127609	$-1 + (234 + (5^6 + 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	1279108	$12 \cdot (3 + 4^5 / (6/7)) \cdot 89$
1127611	$1 + (234 + (5^6 + 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	1280527	$(1 - 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5^6 - 7^8)) / 9$
1128750	$(12+3)^4 + 5^6 \cdot (78-9)$	1280818	$-12^3 / 4 - 5^6 \cdot (7-89)$
1130583	$-1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot (4 - (5^6 + 78) \cdot 9)$	1280869	$(1 - 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot (5+6) - 7^8)) / 9$
1130585	$1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot (4 - (5^6 + 78) \cdot 9)$	1281052	$(1 - 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5^6 / 6 - 7^8)) / 9$
1130647	$-1 + 2^3 \cdot (4 + (5^6 + 78) \cdot 9)$	1281148	$(-1 - 2) \cdot 34 - 5^6 \cdot (7-89)$
1130649	$1 + 2^3 \cdot (4 + (5^6 + 78) \cdot 9)$	1281162	$(1 - 23) \cdot 4 - 5^6 \cdot (7-89)$
1138167	$(-1 + (2^3)^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7/8)) \cdot 9$	1281190	$(-12 - 3) \cdot 4 - 5^6 \cdot (7-89)$
1138185	$(1 + (2^3)^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7/8)) \cdot 9$	1281216	$1^2 \cdot -34 - 5^6 \cdot (7-89)$
1142775	$(-1 + (2^3)^4 \cdot (5^6 - 7 + 8)) \cdot 9$	1281233	$-1/2 \cdot 34 - 5^6 \cdot (7-89)$
1142793	$(1 + (2^3)^4 \cdot (5^6 - 7 + 8)) \cdot 9$	1281267	$1/2 \cdot 34 - 5^6 \cdot (7-89)$
1155025	$(-1 + 2^3 \cdot (3 + 4 + 5) \cdot 6) \cdot (7^8 - 9)$	1281284	$1^2 \cdot 34 - 5^6 \cdot (7-89)$
1155119	$(1 + 2^3 \cdot (3 + 4 + 5) \cdot 6) \cdot (7^8 - 9)$	1281310	$(12+3) \cdot 4 - 5^6 \cdot (7-89)$
1166665	$(1 - (2 - 3^4 / 5^6 - 7) \cdot 8) / 9$	1281338	$(-1 + 23) \cdot 4 - 5^6 \cdot (7-89)$
1185209	$(1 + 23^4 \cdot (5+67)) / (8+9)$	1281352	$(1+2) \cdot 34 - 5^6 \cdot (7-89)$
1201713	$-1 \cdot 2 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 789)$	1281394	$12 \cdot 3^4 - 5^6 \cdot (7-89)$
1201714	$-1 \cdot 2 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 789)$	1281607	$(1 + 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5^6 + 7^8)) / 9$
1201715	$1 \cdot 2 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 789)$	1281682	$12^3 / 4 - 5^6 \cdot (7-89)$
1201717	$1^2 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 789)$	1287880	$-12 - (3^4 + 5^6) \cdot (7-89)$
1201718	$1^2 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 789)$	1287904	$12 - (3^4 + 5^6) \cdot (7-89)$
1201719	$1 + 2 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 789)$	1304628	$-12 \cdot ((3^4 - 5^6) \cdot 7 + 89)$
1208261	$(-1 + (2^3)^4 \cdot 5^6) \cdot (6^7 + 8 + 9)$	1306764	$-12 \cdot ((3^4 - 5^6) \cdot 7 - 89)$
1208379	$(1 + (2^3)^4 \cdot 5^6) \cdot (6^7 + 8 + 9)$	1310460	$-12 \cdot (3^4 - 5^6 \cdot 7 + 89)$
1208751	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 78 \cdot 9)$	1311439	$-12 \cdot (3^4 - 5^6 \cdot 7) - 89$
1215150	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 7 \cdot 89)$	1311617	$-12 \cdot (3^4 - 5^6 \cdot 7) + 89$
1215174	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 - 7 \cdot 89)$	1312245	$12 + 3 \cdot (4 \cdot 5^6 \cdot 7 - 89)$
1217570	$(1 + (2+3)^4) \cdot ((5^6 + 7) / 8 - 9)$	1312267	$12 \cdot (-3^4 + 5^6 \cdot 7) - 89$
1223645	$(1 + 2/3) \cdot (-4 + 5^6) \cdot (7^8 - 9)$	1312275	$(1 + 2) \cdot (-3 + 4 \cdot 5^6 \cdot 7 - 8 \cdot 9)$
1223703	$(1 + (2 - 3^4 \cdot 5^6) \cdot 7^8) \cdot 9$	1312377	$(1 - 2) \cdot 3 \cdot (4 \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 8) + 9)$
1223721	$(1 - (2 - 3^4 \cdot 5^6) \cdot 7^8) \cdot 9$	1312445	$12 \cdot (-3^4 + 5^6 \cdot 7) + 89$
1223965	$(1 + 2/3) \cdot (4 + 5^6 \cdot (7^8 - 9))$	1312555	$12 \cdot (3^4 + 5^6 \cdot 7) - 89$
1224567	$(1 + (2 - 3^4 \cdot 5^6 \cdot 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	1312623	$(-1 + 2) \cdot 3 \cdot (4 \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 8) + 9)$
1224873	$(1 + (2 + 3^4 \cdot 5^6 \cdot 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	1312725	$(1 + 2) \cdot (3 + 4 / 5^6 - 6^7 + 8 \cdot 9)$
1225719	$(-1 + (2 + 3^4 \cdot 5^6) \cdot 7^8) \cdot 9$	1312733	$12 \cdot (3^4 + 5^6 \cdot 7) + 89$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1313383	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7)-89$	1454009	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6+7*8+9)$
1313561	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7)+89$	1454151	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6+7*8+9)$
1314540	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7+89)$	1459629	$(-1+(2+3^4)^*(5^6+7)/8)^*9$
1316076	$-12+3^4*(5^6+7*89)$	1459647	$(1+(2+3^4)^*(5^6+7)/8)^*9$
1316100	$12+3^4*(5^6+7*89)$	1468681	$-1-2^*(34-5^6*(7*8-9))$
1318236	$12^*((3^4+5^6)*7-89)$	1468683	$1-2^*(34-5^6*(7*8-9))$
1320372	$12^*((3^4+5^6)*7+89)$	1468817	$-1+2^*(34+5^6*(7*8-9))$
1322475	$-12+3^4*(5^6+7*89)$	1468819	$1+2^*(34+5^6*(7*8-9))$
1322499	$12+3^4*(5^6+7*89)$	1471527	$(-1+((2^3)^4*5-6*7)^*8)^*9$
1329531	$-1-2+3^4*(5^6+7*89)$	1471545	$(1+((2^3)^4*5-6*7)^*8)^*9$
1329532	$-1*2+3^4*(5^6+7*89)$	1477575	$(-1+((2^3)^4*5+6*7)^*8)^*9$
1329533	$1-2+3^4*(5^6+7*89)$	1492212	$-12-(3^4-5^6)^*(7+89)$
1329535	$1^2+3^4*(5^6+7*89)$	1494967	$(1-(2^3)^4*5)^*(6-7-8*9)$
1329536	$1^*2+3^4*(5^6+7*89)$	1495113	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(-6+7+8*9)$
1329537	$1+2+3^4*(5^6+7*89)$	1499301	$(1-2)^*-3*(4*(5^6-7)^*8-9)$
1331875	$(12+3)^4-5^6*(7-89)$	1499355	$(1-2)^*-3*(4*(5^6-7)^*8+9)$
1352316	$-12-(3^4-5^6)^*(7+89)$	1499796	$(1+2)^*(-3+(4*5^6-7)^*8-9)$
1352340	$12-(3^4-5^6)^*(7+89)$	1499898	$(-1-2)^*34+5^6*(7+89)$
1352463	$-12^3*4+5^6*(7+89)$	1499912	$(1-23)^*4+5^6*(7+89)$
1356800	$(1+2/3)/(4^5-5/(6+7*89))$	1499966	$1^2*-34+5^6*(7+89)$
1357643	$-12^3-4+5^6*(7+89)$	1500034	$1^2*34+5^6*(7+89)$
1357651	$-12^3+4+5^6*(7+89)$	1500088	$(-1+23)^*4+5^6*(7+89)$
1357965	$-1+23^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1500102	$(1+2)^*34+5^6*(7+89)$
1357966	$1^*23^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1500204	$(1+2)^*(3+(4*5^6+7)^*8+9)$
1357967	$1+23^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1500645	$(1-2)^*-3*(4*(5^6+7)^*8-9)$
1358943	$-12^3/4+5^6*(7+89)$	1500699	$(1-2)^*-3*(4*(5^6+7)^*8+9)$
1359231	$-12^*3^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1507764	$-12+(3^4+5^6)^*(7+89)$
1359273	$(-1-2)^*34+5^6*(7+89)$	1507788	$12+(3^4+5^6)^*(7+89)$
1359279	$(1+23)^*-4+5^6*(7+89)$	1515506	$(1-23)^4-5^6*(7-89)$
1359282	$-1-23^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1536852	$(-12+3^4-4*5^6*7)^*89$
1359283	$-1^*23^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1537908	$-12+3^4-4*5^6*7*89$
1359284	$1-23^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1537932	$12+3^4-4*5^6*7*89$
1359315	$(-12-3)^*4+5^6*(7+89)$	1538988	$(12+3^4-4*5^6*7)^*89$
1359341	$1^2*-34+5^6*(7+89)$	1550625	$(12+3)^4+5^6*(7+89)$
1359358	$-1/2^*34+5^6*(7+89)$	1561501	$(-1+2^*3^4*5^6)^*(8+9)$
1359392	$1/2^*34+5^6*(7+89)$	1561535	$(1+2^*3^4*5^6)^*(8+9)$
1359409	$1^2^*34+5^6*(7+89)$	1562317	$(1+2^*(3^4*5^6+7^8))/9$
1359435	$(12+3)^*4+5^6*(7+89)$	1574172	$(-1+(23^4*5+67)/8)^*9$
1359466	$-1+23^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1574190	$(1+(23^4*5+67)/8)^*9$
1359467	$1^*23^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1597375	$(-1+2^*(3+4+5)^*6)^*(7*8+9)$
1359468	$1+23^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1597505	$(1+2^*(3+4+5)^*6)^*(7*8+9)$
1359471	$(1+23)^*4+5^6*(7+89)$	1613026	$(1+23)^4-5^6*(7-89)$
1359477	$(1+2)^*34+5^6*(7+89)$	1624028	$-12^*(3^4-5^6*7/89)$
1359519	$12^*3^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1624856	$12^*(-3^4+5^6*7/89)$
1359807	$12^3/4+5^6*(7+89)$	1624892	$-12^*(3^4-5^6*7/89)$
1360347	$12^*3^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1624916	$12^*(-3-4+5^6*7/89)$
1361099	$12^3-4+5^6*(7+89)$	1624984	$12^*(-3^4+5^6*7/89)$
1361107	$12^3+4+5^6*(7+89)$	1625016	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7/89)$
1366287	$12^3*4+5^6*(7+89)$	1625084	$12^*(3+4+5^6*7/89)$
1366410	$-12+(3^4+5^6)^*(7+89)$	1625108	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7/89)$
1366434	$12+(3^4+5^6)^*(7+89)$	1625144	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7/89)$
1370880	$12^*(3-4+5)^*(67-8/9)$	1625972	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7/89)$
1389285	$(1+(2-3^4)^*(5^6+7)/8)^*-9$	1639215	$-1+23^4+5^6*(7+89)$
1389303	$(1-(2-3^4)^*(5^6+7)/8)^*9$	1639216	$1^*23^4+5^6*(7+89)$
1395666	$(12+3/4)^*(5^6*7+89)$	1639217	$1+23^4+5^6*(7+89)$
1396123	$-12-(3^4-4-5)^*6^7-89$	1639230	$(12+3)^*(-4+5^6*7-89)$
1396147	$12-(3^4-4-5)^*6^7-89$	1639350	$(12+3)^*(4+5^6*7-89)$
1396301	$-12-(3^4-4-5)^*6^7+89$	1640534	$(1-2^3)^*(4-5^6*(7+8)+9)$
1396325	$12-(3^4-4-5)^*6^7+89$	1640590	$(1+2^3)^*(4+5^6*(7+8)-9)$
1403035	$-12+(3^4-4+5)^*6^7-89$	1640660	$(1-2^3)^*(4-5^6*(7+8)-9)$
1403059	$12+(3^4-4+5)^*6^7-89$	1640716	$(1+2^3)^*(4+5^6*(7+8)+9)$
1403213	$-12+(3^4-4+5)^*6^7+89$	1641900	$(12+3)^*(-4+5^6*7+89)$
1403237	$12+(3^4-4+5)^*6^7+89$	1642020	$(12+3)^*(4+5^6*7+89)$
1405209	$(-1+2^*3^4*(5+6))^*789$	1678932	$12^*(-3^4+(5^6-7)^*9)$
1406787	$(1+2^*3^4*(5+6))^*789$	1685406	$12+3^*(4*5^6-7)^*9$
1407744	$12^*(3-4+5)^*(67+8/9)$	1686483	$(-1+2^*(3/4/5^6-6-7)^*8)^*9$
1409901	$(1+23)^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1686786	$-12+(3^4*5^6-7)^*9$
1410000	$(12+3)^4+5^6*(7+89)$	1686810	$12+(3^4*5^6-7)^*9$
1411635	$(1+(2-(3+4)^5/(6/7))^*8)^*-9$	1688214	$12+(3^4*5^6+7)^*9$
1411941	$(1+(2+(3+4)^5/(6/7))^*8)^*9$	1688517	$(1+2^*(3/4/5^6-6+7)^*8)^*9$
1423179	$(1+(2-3^4*(5^6-7))/8)^*-9$	1689594	$-12+3^*(4*5^6+7)^*9$
1423197	$(1-(2-3^4*(5^6-7))/8)^*9$	1689618	$12+3^*(4*5^6+7)^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1691151	$(1+23)^{4+5^6*(78+9)}$	2119965	$(12+3)*(4+(5^6+78)^9)$
1695780	$12^*(-3^4+(5^6+78)^9)$	2131236	$(-1+(2^3*3^4+5^6)^*(7+8))^9$
1695840	$12^*(-3-4+(5^6+78)^9)$	2131254	$(1+(2^3*3^4+5^6)^*(7+8))^9$
1695912	$-12+3^4*(5^6+78)^9$	2156087	$-1-2^*(3^4-5^6*(78-9))$
1695936	$12+3^4*(5^6+78)^9$	2156089	$1-2^*(3^4-5^6*(78-9))$
1696008	$12^*(3+4+(5^6+78)^9)$	2156157	$-1-23^*(4-5^6*(7+8-9))$
1696068	$12^*(3^4+(5^6+78)^9)$	2156159	$1-23^*(4-5^6*(7+8-9))$
1719816	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5/6)^{7*8*9}$	2156182	$1^2*(-34+5^6*(78-9))$
1720824	$(1+(2^3)^4*5/6)^{7*8*9}$	2156183	$1-2^*(34-5^6*(78-9))$
1734256	$(1-23)^{4+5^6*(7+89)}$	2156263	$-1+2^*(3+4+5^6*(78-9))$
1740715	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6+7+8^9)$	2156317	$-1+2^*(34+5^6*(78-9))$
1740885	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6+7+8^9)$	2156318	$1^2*(34+5^6*(78-9))$
1793589	$(1+2)^*((3^4(4^5-6)+7)/8-9)$	2156341	$-1+23^*(4+5^6*(7+8-9))$
1793643	$(1+2)^*((3^4(4^5-6)+7)/8+9)$	2156343	$1+23^*(4+5^6*(7+8-9))$
1831776	$(1+23)^{4+5^6*(7+89)}$	2156411	$-1+2^*(3^4+5^6*(78-9))$
1840080	$(1+(2^3*3^4-5^6)^7)^*(-8-9)$	2156413	$1+2^*(3^4+5^6*(78-9))$
1840114	$(1-(2^3*3^4-5^6)^7)^*(8+9)$	2176541	$(1+23)^4*(5-67-8)/-9$
1858514	$(1-2^3)^*(4-(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	2202882	$(1+2)^*(-3^4+5^6*(7^8-9))$
1858570	$(1+2^3)^*(4+(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	2203089	$(1+2)^*(3^*-4+5^6*(7^8-9))$
1860180	$(1-2^3)^*(4-(5^6+7)^*(8+9))$	2203101	$-12-3^*(4-5^6*(7^8-9))$
1860236	$(1+2^3)^*(4+(5^6+7)^*(8+9))$	2203113	$(1-2)^3*(4-5^6*(7^8-9))$
1878636	$(-1+(2^3*3^4+5^6)^7)^*(8+9)$	2203137	$1^2*3^*(4+5^6*(7^8-9))$
1878670	$(1+(2^3*3^4+5^6)^7)^*(8+9)$	2203149	$12+3^*(4+5^6*(7^8-9))$
1916149	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+(5^6-7^8)/9)$	2203161	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6*(7^8-9))$
1916356	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+(5^6-7^8)/9)$	2203368	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6*(7^8-9))$
1916368	$-12-3^*(4+(5^6-7^8)/9)$	2218176	$12^3*(4^5/(6/7)+89)$
1916416	$12+3^*(4-(5^6-7^8)/9)$	2247525	$(1+2^*(3^4-(5^6-7)^8))^*-9$
1916428	$(1+2)^*(3^4-(5^6-7^8)/9)$	2248965	$(-1+2^*(3-4+(5^6-7)^8))^9$
1916635	$(1+2)^*(3^4-(5^6-7^8)/9)$	2249019	$(1-2^*(3-4-(5^6-7)^8))^9$
1941425	$(-1+2^3(3+4+5)^6)^*(7+8^9)$	2249541	$(1+2^*(3^4-(5^6+7)^8))^*-9$
1941583	$(1+2^3(3+4+5)^6)^*(7+8^9)$	2249559	$(1-2^*(3^4-(5^6+7)^8))^9$
1945505	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5)^*((6+7)^8-9)$	2250441	$(-1+2^*(3^4+(5^6-7)^8))^9$
1945695	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*((6+7)^8-9)$	2250459	$(1+2^*(3^4+(5^6-7)^8))^9$
1967139	$(1+2^*(3^4-5^6*7+8))^*-9$	2250783	$(1+2^*(3^4-(5^6+7)^8))^*-9$
1967427	$(1+2^*(3^4-5^6*7-8))^*-9$	2250801	$(1-2^*(3^4-(5^6+7)^8))^9$
1967445	$(1-2^*(3^4-5^6*7-8))^9$	2250981	$(-1+2^*(3-4+(5^6+7)^8))^9$
1968399	$(1-2^*(3^4-5^6*7+8))^9$	2251035	$(1-2^*(3-4-(5^6+7)^8))^9$
1969101	$(-1+2^*(3^4+5^6*7+8))^9$	2252475	$(1+2^*(3^4+(5^6+7)^8))^9$
1970055	$(-1+2^*(3^4+5^6*7-8))^9$	2255790	$1/23^*(-45+6+7^8*9)$
1970073	$(1+2^*(3^4+5^6*7-8))^9$	2260647	$(-1+2^*(3^4+5^6-7)^8)^9$
1970361	$(1+2^*(3^4+5^6*7+8))^9$	2260665	$(1+2^*(3^4+5^6-7)^8)^9$
1978803	$(-1+2^*((3^4+5^6)^7*8))^9$	2261906	$1/(23/(4+(5^6+7^8)^9))$
1979109	$(1+2^*((3^4+5^6)^7*8))^9$	2262663	$(-1+2^*(3^4+5^6+7)^8)^9$
2015467	$-1/(2+3)+(4/5/6^7-8)^9$	2262681	$(1+2^*(3^4+5^6+7)^8)^9$
2015611	$-1/(2+3)+(4/5/6^7-8)^9$	2290311	$(-1+2/(3-4/5)^*(6^7-8))^9$
2027619	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6*(7+8)^9)$	2290329	$(1+2/(3-4/5)^*(6^7-8))^9$
2031181	$-1-2^*(34+5^6*(7-8^9))$	2296680	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^*(5^6*7-8)-9)$
2031183	$1-2^*(34+5^6*(7-8^9))$	2296734	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^*(5^6*7-8)+9)$
2031317	$-1+2^*(34+5^6*(7^8+9))$	2296824	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^*5^6*7-8-9)$
2031319	$1+2^*(34+5^6*(7^8+9))$	2296872	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^*5^6*7+8-9)$
2033655	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5/6-7^8))^*-9$	2296878	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^*5^6*7-8+9)$
2033673	$(1-(2^3)^4*(5/6-7^8))^9$	2296926	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^*5^6*7+8+9)$
2049255	$(-1+((2^3)^4-5^6)^7*8)^9$	2297016	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^*(5^6*7+8)-9)$
2049273	$(1+((2^3)^4-5^6)^7*8)^9$	2297070	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^*(5^6*7+8)+9)$
2076433	$-1+(23-4)^*(5^6*7-89)$	2314127	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5)^*((6+7)^8+9)$
2076435	$1+(23-4)^*(5^6*7-89)$	2314353	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*((6+7)^8+9)$
2079495	$(-1+((2^3)^4+5^6)^7*8)^9$	2334606	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6^7+8^9)$
2079513	$(1+((2^3)^4+5^6)^7*8)^9$	2334834	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6^7+8^9)$
2079815	$-1+(23-4)^*(5^6*7+89)$	2403000	$(1+(2-3^4*5)^67)^*-89$
2079817	$1+(23-4)^*(5^6*7+89)$	2403178	$(1-(2-3^4*5)^67)^*89$
2087496	$(1+(2^3*3^4-5^6)^*(7+8))^*-9$	2404204	$(1-23)^*(4-5^6*7+89)$
2087514	$(1-(2^3*3^4-5^6)^*(7+8))^9$	2404380	$(-1+23)^*(4+5^6*7-89)$
2095095	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5/6+7^8))^9$	2408120	$(1-23)^*(4-5^6*7-89)$
2095113	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5/6+7^8))^9$	2408296	$(-1+23)^*(4+5^6*7+89)$
2098785	$(12+3)^*(-4+(5^6-78)^9)$	2424845	$-1-2^*((3^4-5^6)^7+8+9)$
2098905	$(12+3)^*(4+(5^6-78)^9)$	2424847	$1-2^*((3^4-5^6)^7+8+9)$
2107268	$-1-(234-5^6*(7+8))^9$	2424881	$-1-2^*((3^4-5^6)^7+8-9)$
2107270	$1-(234-5^6*(7+8))^9$	2424883	$1-2^*((3^4-5^6)^7+8-9)$
2111480	$-1+(234+5^6*(7+8))^9$	2425296	$(1+(23^4+5/6)^7*8)/9$
2111482	$1+(234+5^6*(7+8))^9$	2426852	$(-1+(2+3^4*5)^67)^*89$
2117585	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(7^8-9)$	2427030	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^67)^*89$
2119845	$(12+3)^*(-4+(5^6+78)^9)$	2437319	$-1-2^*(3^4-5^6*7+8+9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2437321	$1-2^*(3^4-5^6*78+9)$	2543867	$-1+2^*(3^4*(5^6+78)-9)$
2437355	$-1-2^*(3^4-5^6*78-9)$	2543869	$1+2^*(3^4*(5^6+78)-9)$
2437357	$1-2^*(3^4-5^6*78-9)$	2543903	$-1+2^*(3^4*(5^6+78)+9)$
2437414	$1^*2^*(-34+5^6*78-9)$	2543905	$1+2^*(3^4*(5^6+78)+9)$
2437415	$1-2^*(34-5^6*78+9)$	2546011	$(1+(2^*3)^4)*((5^6+7)/8+9)$
2437422	$-1-2^*(34-5^6*78-9)$	2559875	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5)*(6+7*(8+9))$
2437424	$1-2^*(34-5^6*78)-9$	2560125	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)*(6+7*(8+9))$
2437440	$-1-2^*(34-5^6*78)+9$	2562339	$1-2^*(3^4+5^6*(7-89))$
2437442	$1-2^*(34-5^6*78)+9$	2562431	$-1-2^*(34+5^6*(7-89))$
2437449	$-1-2^*(34-5^6*78-9)$	2562432	$-1^*2^*(34+5^6*(7-89))$
2437450	$1^*2^*(-34+5^6*78+9)$	2562433	$1-2^*(34+5^6*(7-89))$
2437451	$1-2^*(34-5^6*78-9)$	2562487	$1-2^*(3+4+5^6*(7-89))$
2437531	$-1+2^*(3+4+5^6*78+9)$	2562567	$-1+2^*(34-5^6*(7-89))$
2437549	$-1+2^*(34+5^6*78-9)$	2562568	$1^*2^*(34-5^6*(7-89))$
2437550	$1^*2^*(34+5^6*78-9)$	2562569	$1+2^*(34-5^6*(7-89))$
2437551	$1+2^*(34+5^6*78-9)$	2562661	$-1+2^*(3^4-5^6*(7-89))$
2437558	$-1+2^*(34+5^6*78)-9$	2564361	$(-1+2^3*4^5*6)/(7-8/9)$
2437560	$1+2^*(34+5^6*78)-9$	2576367	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5*(6+7))^*(8+9)$
2437576	$-1+2^*(34+5^6*78)+9$	2576401	$(1+(2^3)^4*5*(6+7))^*(8+9)$
2437578	$1+2^*(34+5^6*78)+9$	2622768	$(1+2^3)*(-4+5^6*7-89)$
2437585	$-1+2^*(34+5^6*78+9)$	2623029	$(1+2)*((-3^4+5^6*7)^8-9)$
2437586	$1^*2^*(34+5^6*78+9)$	2623083	$(1+2)*((-3^4+5^6*7)^8+9)$
2437643	$-1+2^*(3^4+5^6*78-9)$	2624685	$(1+2)*((3^*-4+5^6*7)^8-9)$
2437645	$1+2^*(3^4+5^6*78-9)$	2624730	$(1+2)*(-3^4+5^6*7^8-9)$
2437679	$-1+2^*(3^4+5^6*78+9)$	2624739	$(1+2)*((3^*-4+5^6*7)^8+9)$
2437681	$1+2^*(3^4+5^6*78+9)$	2624784	$(1+2)*(-3^4+5^6*7^8+9)$
2450117	$-1+2^*((3^4+5^6)*78-9)$	2624868	$(-1-2)^*(3+(4-5^6*7)^8+9)$
2450119	$1+2^*((3^4+5^6)*78-9)$	2624877	$1^2*3^*((-4+5^6*7)^8-9)$
2450153	$-1+2^*((3^4+5^6)*78+9)$	2624931	$1^2*3^*((-4+5^6*7)^8+9)$
2450155	$1+2^*((3^4+5^6)*78+9)$	2624940	$(1+2)*((3^4-5^6*7)^8+9)$
2456382	$(1+2^3*4^5*(5-6-78))/-9$	2625060	$(1+2)*(-3+(4+5^6*7)^8-9)$
2459097	$(1+(2-3^4*5)^6*78)^*-9$	2625069	$(-1+2)^*3^*((4+5^6*7)^8-9)$
2459115	$(1-(2-3^4*5)^6*78)^*9$	2625123	$(-1+2)^*3^*((4+5^6*7)^8+9)$
2468681	$-1-2^*(34-5^6*(7+8*9))$	2625132	$(1+2)*((3^4+5^6*7)^8+9)$
2468683	$1-2^*(34-5^6*(7+8*9))$	2625216	$(1+2)*((3^4+5^6*7)^8-9)$
2468817	$-1+2^*(34+5^6*(7+8*9))$	2625261	$(1+2)*((3^4+5^6*7)^8-9)$
2468819	$1+2^*(34+5^6*(7+8*9))$	2625270	$(1+2)*((3^4+5^6*7)^8+9)$
2483505	$(-1+(2+3^4*5)^6*78)^*9$	2625315	$(1+2)*((3^4+5^6*7)^8+9)$
2483523	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^6*78)^*9$	2626917	$(1+2)*((3^4+5^6*7)^8-9)$
2513485	$-1-2^3*(4-5^6*7+89)$	2626971	$(1+2)*((3^4+5^6*7)^8+9)$
2513486	$1^*2^3*(-4+5^6*7-89)$	2627040	$(1+2^3)*(-4+5^6*7+89)$
2513487	$1-2^3*(4-5^6*7+89)$	2627232	$(1+2^3)*((4+5^6*7+89)$
2513669	$-1+2^3*(4+5^6*7-89)$	2638581	$(1+2)*((3^4+5^6)^7*8-9)$
2513670	$1^*2^3*(4+5^6*7-89)$	2638635	$(1+2)*((3^4+5^6)^7*8+9)$
2513671	$1+2^3*(4+5^6*7-89)$	2641791	$(1-(2^3)^4*5)^*(6-(7+8)^9)$
2514060	$-1+2^3*(4+5^6*7-8*9)$	2642049	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(-6+(7+8)^9)$
2515443	$-1-2^3*(4-5^6*7)-89$	2667673	$(-1+2^3*4^5*(5+6^7))/8+9$
2515621	$-1-2^3*(4-5^6*7)+89$	2691063	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5*(6+7+8))^*9$
2515623	$1-2^3*(4-5^6*7)+89$	2691081	$(1+(2^3)^4*5*(6+7+8))^*9$
2515629	$1+2^3*(4+5^6*7)-89$	2692331	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5/6)^*789$
2515693	$-1+2^3*(4+5^6*7+8-9)$	2718587	$-1-2^*(3^4-5^6*(78+9))$
2515805	$-1+2^3*(4+5^6*7)+89$	2718589	$1-2^*(3^4-5^6*(78+9))$
2515807	$1+2^3*(4+5^6*7)+89$	2718681	$-1-2^*(34-5^6*(78+9))$
2516107	$-1+2^3*(4+5^6*7+8+9)$	2718682	$1^*2^*(34+5^6*(78+9))$
2516109	$1+2^3*(4+5^6*7+8+9)$	2718683	$1-2^*(34-5^6*(78+9))$
2517009	$(1+((2^3)^4-56)^7)^*89$	2718725	$-1-2^*(3^4-5^6*(78+9))$
2517580	$1^*2^3*(-4+5^6*7+89)$	2718737	$1-2^*(3+4-5^6*(78+9))$
2517581	$1-2^3*(4-5^6*7-89)$	2718747	$-1+2^*(3-4+5^6*(78+9))$
2517763	$-1+2^3*(4+5^6*7+89)$	2718763	$-1+2^*(3+4+5^6*(78+9))$
2517764	$1^*2^3*(4+5^6*7+89)$	2718765	$1+2^*(3+4+5^6*(78+9))$
2517765	$1+2^3*(4+5^6*7+89)$	2718817	$-1+2^*(34+5^6*(78+9))$
2529937	$-1+2^*(3^4*(5^6-7)-89)$	2718818	$1^*2^*(34+5^6*(78+9))$
2529939	$1+2^*(3^4*(5^6-7)-89)$	2718819	$1+2^*(34+5^6*(78+9))$
2530293	$-1+2^*(3^4*(5^6-7)+89)$	2718911	$-1+2^*(3^4+5^6*(78+9))$
2530295	$1+2^*(3^4*(5^6-7)+89)$	2718913	$1+2^*(3^4+5^6*(78+9))$
2532205	$-1+2^*(3^4*(5^6+7)-89)$	2732575	$(1+2^3*3^4)*((5^6*7-8)^9)$
2532207	$1+2^*(3^4*(5^6+7)-89)$	2733950	$(1+2^3*3^4)*((5^6*7-8-9)$
2532561	$-1+2^*(3^4*(5^6+7)+89)$	2734350	$(1+2^3*3^4)*((5^6*7+8-9)$
2532563	$1+2^*(3^4*(5^6+7)+89)$	2734400	$(1+2^3*3^4)*((5^6*7+8+9)$
2542085	$(-1+(2^*3)^4)*((5^6+7)/8+9)$	2734800	$(1+2^3*3^4)*((5^6*7+8+9)$
2543607	$(-1+(2^3)^4)*((5+6)^7-8)^*9$	2736175	$(1+2^3*3^4)*((5^6*7+8)^9)$
2543625	$(1+(2^3)^4)*((5+6)^7-8)^*9$	2757741	$(12^*3)^4+5^6*(78-9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2779841	$-1 \cdot 2^*(3^4 - (5^6 - 7)^*89)$	3046911	$(1+2)^*(3^4 - 5^6*(7-8^9))$
2779843	$1 \cdot 2^*(3^4 - (5^6 - 7)^*89)$	3047118	$(1+2)^*(3^4 + 5^6*(7^8 + 9))$
2779979	$-1 \cdot 2^*(3^4 - (5^6 - 7)^*89)$	3061996	$(-1+2^3)^*(4/5^6 - 6^7 - 8^9)$
2779991	$1 \cdot 2^*(3+4 - (5^6 - 7)^*89)$	3062213	$(-1+2^3)^*(4*(5^6*7-8)-9)$
2780001	$-1 \cdot 2^*(3-4 + (5^6 - 7)^*89)$	3062339	$(-1+2^3)^*(4*(5^6*7-8)+9)$
2780017	$-1 \cdot 2^*(3+4 + (5^6 - 7)^*89)$	3062381	$(-1+2^3)^*(4*5^6*7-8-9)$
2780019	$1 \cdot 2^*(3+4 + (5^6 - 7)^*89)$	3062493	$(-1+2^3)^*(4*5^6*7+8-9)$
2780165	$-1 \cdot 2^*(3^4 + (5^6 - 7)^*89)$	3062507	$(-1+2^3)^*(4*5^6*7-8+9)$
2780167	$1 \cdot 2^*(3^4 + (5^6 - 7)^*89)$	3062619	$(-1+2^3)^*(4*5^6*7+8+9)$
2782333	$-1 \cdot 2^*(3^4 - (5^6 + 7)^*89)$	3062661	$(-1+2^3)^*(4*(5^6*7+8)-9)$
2782335	$1 \cdot 2^*(3^4 - (5^6 + 7)^*89)$	3062787	$(-1+2^3)^*(4*(5^6*7+8)+9)$
2782509	$-1 \cdot 2^*(3+4 + (5^6 + 7)^*89)$	3063004	$(-1+2^3)^*(4/5^6 - 6^7 + 8^9)$
2782657	$-1 \cdot 2^*(3^4 + (5^6 + 7)^*89)$	3078218	$(1-23)^*(4 - (5^6 - 78)^9)$
2782659	$1 \cdot 2^*(3^4 + (5^6 + 7)^*89)$	3078394	$(-1+23)^*(4 + (5^6 - 78)^9)$
2792269	$-1 \cdot 2^*((3^4 - 4 - 5)^*6^7 + 89)$	3092355	$(-1 + (2+3/4)^*(5^6 - 7)^8)^*9$
2792271	$1 \cdot 2^*((3^4 - 4 - 5)^*6^7 + 89)$	3092373	$(1 + (2+3/4)^*(5^6 - 7)^8)^*9$
2792627	$-1 \cdot 2^*((3^4 - 4 - 5)^*6^7 - 89)$	3095127	$(-1 + (2+3/4)^*(5^6 + 7)^8)^*9$
2836089	$(1 + (2^3)^4 - 56)^*78)^*9$	3095145	$(1 + (2+3/4)^*(5^6 + 7)^8)^*9$
2843541	$-1 + 23^4*(5^6*7-8)/9$	3109106	$(1-23)^*(4 - (5^6 + 78)^9)$
2843543	$1 + 23^4*(5^6*7-8)/9$	3109282	$(-1+23)^*(4 + (5^6 + 78)^9)$
2843957	$-1 + 23^4*(5^6*7+8)/9$	3114573	$(-1-23)^*(4 - 5^6*78)/9$
2843959	$1 + 23^4*(5^6*7+8)/9$	3123375	$(1+2^3*4)^*((5^6-7)^8-9)$
2848923	$(-1+2^3*4^4*(5^6+7)/8)^*9$	3123825	$(1+2^3*4)^*((5^6-7)^8+9)$
2848941	$(1+2^3*4^4*(5^6+7)/8)^*9$	3126175	$(1+2^3*4)^*((5^6+7)^8-9)$
2873596	$-1+23^4*(4+(5^6-7)^8-9)$	3126625	$(1+2^3*4)^*((5^6+7)^8+9)$
2874010	$-1+23^4*(4+(5^6-7)^8+9)$	3133431	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5+6)^7+8)^*9$
2874012	$1+23^4*(4+(5^6-7)^8+9)$	3133449	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+6)^7+8)^*9$
2874907	$-1 \cdot 23^4*(4-5^6*(7-8+9))$	3170295	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5^6+7^8))^*9$
2874909	$1 \cdot 23^4*(4-5^6*(7-8+9))$	3179616	$(12^3)^4 + 5^6*(7+89)$
2875091	$-1+23^4*(4+5^6*(7-8+9))$	3182859	$(1+(2-3^4*56)^78)^*9$
2875093	$1+23^4*(4+5^6*(7-8+9))$	3182877	$(1-(2-3^4*56)^78)^*9$
2876586	$-1+23^4*(4+(5^6+7)^8+9)$	3185667	$(-1+(2+3^4*56)^78)^*9$
2887539	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6+(7+8)^9)$	3185685	$(1+(2+3^4*56)^78)^*9$
2887821	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6+(7+8)^9)$	3187152	$(1+2)^*(3+(4^5*5^6-7)^*(8+9))$
2928575	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(7^8+9)$	3187848	$(1+2)^*(-3+(4^5*5^6+7)^*(8+9))$
2928705	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(7^8+9)$	3187866	$(1+2)^*(3+(4^5*5^6+7)^*(8+9))$
2950721	$-1+(23+4)^*(5^6*7-89)$	3191259	$(1+2)^*(3+4/5)^*(6^7+8-9)$
2950723	$1+(23+4)^*(5^6*7-89)$	3195036	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(67+89)$
2952897	$(1-2)^*3*(4-(5^6*7-8)^9)$	3218136	$-1-23^4*(4-(5^6-78)^9)$
2952921	$1^2*3*(4+(5^6*7-8)^9)$	3218137	$1^2*3*(-4+(5^6-78)^9)$
2953329	$(1-2)^*3*(4-(5^6*7+8)^9)$	3218138	$1-23^4*(4-(5^6-78)^9)$
2953353	$1^2*3*(4+(5^6*7+8)^9)$	3218320	$-1+23^4*(4+(5^6-78)^9)$
2955527	$-1+(23+4)^*(5^6*7+89)$	3218321	$1^2*3*(4+(5^6-78)^9)$
2955529	$1+(23+4)^*(5^6*7+89)$	3218322	$1+23^4*(4+(5^6-78)^9)$
2960866	$(12^3)^4 - 5^6*(7-89)$	3231179	$1-23^4*(4-(5^6-7-8)^9)$
2978112	$12^3*(-4+(5^6-78)/9)$	3231361	$-1+23^4*(4+(5^6-7-8)^9)$
2991936	$12^3*(4+(5^6-78)/9)$	3231363	$1+23^4*(4+(5^6-7-8)^9)$
2999837	$-1 \cdot 2^*(3^4 - 5^6*(7+89))$	3234273	$(1+2)^*(-34+5^6*(78-9))$
2999839	$1 \cdot 2^*(3^4 - 5^6*(7+89))$	3234351	$-12-3^4*(4-5^6*(78-9))$
2999931	$-1 \cdot 2^*(34-5^6*(7+89))$	3234399	$12+3^4*(4+5^6*(78-9))$
2999932	$1^2*(34+5^6*(7+89))$	3234477	$(1+2)^*(34+5^6*(78-9))$
2999933	$1 \cdot 2^*(34-5^6*(7+89))$	3234673	$-1+23^4*(4+(5^6-7+8)^9)$
2999975	$-1 \cdot 2^*(3^4-5^6*(7+89))$	3246058	$-1+23^4*(4+(5^6+7^8)^9)$
2999987	$1 \cdot 2^*(3+4-5^6*(7+89))$	3249904	$(1+23)^*(-4+5^6*78/9)$
2999997	$-1+2^*(3-4+5^6*(7+89))$	3250096	$(1+23)^*(4+5^6*78/9)$
3000013	$-1+2^*(3+4+5^6*(7+89))$	3250428	$-1-23^4*(4-(5^6+78)^9)$
3000015	$1+2^*(3+4+5^6*(7+89))$	3250429	$1^2*3*(-4+(5^6+78)^9)$
3000067	$-1+2^*(34+5^6*(7+89))$	3250430	$1-23^4*(4-(5^6+78)^9)$
3000068	$1^2*(34+5^6*(7+89))$	3250612	$-1+23^4*(4+(5^6+78)^9)$
3000069	$1+2^*(34+5^6*(7+89))$	3250613	$1^2*3*(4+(5^6+78)^9)$
3000161	$-1+2^*(3^4+5^6*(7+89))$	3250614	$1+23^4*(4+(5^6+78)^9)$
3000163	$1+2^*(3^4+5^6*(7+89))$	3272687	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5+6^7))^*(8+9)$
3008064	$12^3*(-4+(5^6+78)/9)$	3272721	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+6^7))^*(8+9)$
3021888	$12^3*(4+(5^6+78)/9)$	3281001	$(1+(2/3-4)^*(5^6*7-8))^*9$
3033708	$(12+3^4-4^5*(5^6)^7)/89$	3281019	$(1-(2/3-4)^*(5^6*7-8))^*9$
3038991	$(12^3)^4 + 5^6*(78+9)$	3281481	$(1+(2/3-4)^*(5^6*7+8))^*9$
3046632	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+5^6*(7-8^9))$	3281499	$(1-(2/3-4)^*(5^6*7+8))^*9$
3046839	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6*(7-8^9))$	3306591	$(1+(2-3^4*56)^78)^*9$
3046851	$-12-3^4*(4+5^6*(7-8^9))$	3306599	$-1-(2-3^4*56)^78)^*9$
3046863	$(1-2)^*3*(4-5^6*(7^8+9))$	3306889	$1+(2+3^4*56)^78)^*9$
3046887	$1^2*3*(4+5^6*(7^8+9))$	3306897	$(1+(2+3^4*56)^78)^*9$
3046899	$12+3^4*(4+5^6*(7^8+9))$	3353304	$-12^*(3^4*5-6^7+89)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
3354283	$-12*(3^4*5-6^7)-89$	3778719	$-12-3^4*(5-6^7(7+8-9))$
3354461	$-12*(3^4*5-6^7)+89$	3778743	$12-3^4*(5-6^7(7+8-9))$
3355440	$-12*(3^4*5-6^7-89)$	3779529	$-12+3^4*(5+6^7(7+8-9))$
3357897	$(12+3)*(4/5/6^7-89)$	3779553	$12+3^4*(5+6^7(7+8-9))$
3360567	$(12+3)*(4/(5/6^7)+89)$	3783294	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6-7^8)+9)$
3363024	$12*(3^4*5+6^7-89)$	3793203	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6-7-8)-9)$
3364003	$12*(3^4*5+6^7)-89$	3793257	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6-7-8)+9)$
3364181	$12*(3^4*5+6^7)+89$	3795123	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6-7)-8-9)$
3365160	$12*(3^4*5+6^7+89)$	3795171	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6-7)+8-9)$
3373452	$(1+2)*(3^*-4+(5^6-7)^*8^9)$	3795177	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6-7)-8+9)$
3373476	$(1-2)^*3*(4-(5^6-7)^*8^9)$	3795225	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6-7)+8+9)$
3373500	$1^2*3*(4+(5^6-7)^*8^9)$	3796518	$(1+2)*(3^4*5^6-7^*(8+9))$
3376500	$(1-2)^*3*(4-(5^6+7)^*8^9)$	3796659	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6+7-8)+9)$
3376524	$1^2*3*(4+(5^6+7)^*8^9)$	3796870	$(1+2)*(3^4*5^6-(7+8)/9)$
3376548	$(1+2)*(3^4+(5^6+7)^*8^9)$	3796880	$(1+2)*(3^4*5^6+(7+8)/9)$
3391752	$(1+23)*(4+(5^6+78)^*9)$	3797091	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6-7+8)-9)$
3391944	$(1+23)*(4+(5^6+78)^*9)$	3797232	$(1+2)*(3^4*5^6+7^*(8+9))$
3437644	$12^*3*(4+5^6*(7-8/9))$	3798525	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6+7)-8-9)$
3458893	$12+3/45*(6+7^8*9)$	3798573	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6+7)+8-9)$
3498369	$(-1+2^3)^*(4*(5^6-7)^*8-9)$	3798579	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6+7)-8+9)$
3498495	$(-1+2^3)^*(4*(5^6-7)^*8+9)$	3798627	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6+7)+8+9)$
3499545	$(1+2^3)^*(4/5^6-6-7)^*8-9)$	3800493	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6+7+8)-9)$
3500455	$(1+2^3)^*(4/5^6-6+7)^*8+9)$	3800547	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6+7+8)+9)$
3501505	$(-1+2^3)^*(4*(5^6+7)^*8-9)$	3810456	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6+7^8)-9)$
3501631	$(-1+2^3)^*(4*(5^6+7)^*8+9)$	3810510	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6+7^8)+9)$
3502071	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5+6*(7+8)))^*9)$	3835329	$(1+2/3^4-4^*5^6)^*789$
3502089	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+6*(7+8)))^*9)$	3843648	$(-1-2)^*(34+5^6*(7-89))$
3559345	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(7+8^9)$	3843726	$-12-3*(4+5^6*(7-89))$
3559503	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(7+8^9)$	3843741	$1+2-3*(4+5^6*(7-89))$
3593657	$-1-23*(4+5^6*(7-8-9))$	3843774	$12+3*(4-5^6*(7-89))$
3593659	$1-23*(4+5^6*(7-8-9))$	3843852	$(1+2)*(34-5^6*(7-89))$
3593841	$-1+23*(4-5^6*(7-8-9))$	3934295	$-1+(2+34)*(5^6*7-89)$
3593843	$1+23*(4-5^6*(7-8-9))$	3934297	$1+(2+34)*(5^6*7-89)$
3605148	$(1+2)^*3^4*(5^6-789)$	3934440	$12^*3*(4+5^6*7-89)$
3656121	$(1+2)*(-34+5^6*78-9)$	3936576	$12*(3*(4+5^6*7)-89)$
3656175	$(1+2)*(-34+5^6*78+9)$	3937497	$(1+2)*(3^4/5^6-6^*7+8-9)$
3656199	$-12-3*(4-5^6*78+9)$	3937503	$(1+2)*(3^4/5^6-6^*7+8+9)$
3656217	$-12-3*(4-5^6*78)-9$	3938424	$12*(3*(4+5^6*7)+89)$
3656283	$12+3*(4+5^6*78)+9$	3940560	$12^*3*(-4+5^6*7+89)$
3656286	$-1-2+3*(4+5^6*78+9)$	3940703	$-1+(2+34)*(5^6*7+89)$
3656292	$1+2+3*(4+5^6*78+9)$	3940705	$1+(2+34)*(5^6*7+89)$
3656301	$12+3*(4+5^6*78+9)$	3940848	$12^*3*(4+5^6*7+89)$
3656325	$(1+2)*(34+5^6*78-9)$	3988602	$(1+2)^*3^4*(5^6+789)$
3656379	$(1+2)*(34+5^6*78+9)$	4011384	$(1+2/(3/4/5))^*(6^7-8^9)$
3700186	$(1+23^4/5)^*(67-8/9)$	4013448	$(1+2/(3/4/5))^*(6^7+8^9)$
3702882	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6*(7+8^9))$	4018167	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5+(6+7)^*8))^*9)$
3703089	$(1+2)^*(3^*-4+5^6*(7+8^9))$	4018185	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+(6+7)^*8))^*9)$
3703101	$-12-3*(4-5^6*(7+8^9))$	4078023	$(1+2)*(-34+5^6*(78+9))$
3703113	$(1-2)^*3*(4-5^6*(7+8^9))$	4078101	$-12-3*(4-5^6*(78+9))$
3703137	$1^2*3*(4+5^6*(7+8^9))$	4078116	$1+2-3*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
3703149	$12+3*(4+5^6*(7+8^9))$	4078134	$-1-2+3*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
3703161	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6*(7+8^9))$	4078139	$1^2+3*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
3703368	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6*(7+8^9))$	4078140	$1+2+3*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
3715721	$-1-2+34*(5^6*7-89)$	4078149	$12+3*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
3715722	$-1^2+34*(5^6*7-89)$	4078227	$(1+2)*(34+5^6*(78+9))$
3715723	$1-2+34*(5^6*7-89)$	4115115	$(-1+234*(5^6+7)/8)^*9)$
3715725	$1^2+34*(5^6*7-89)$	4115123	$-1+234*(5^6+7)/8^*9)$
3715727	$1+2+34*(5^6*7-89)$	4115125	$1+234*(5^6+7)/8^*9)$
3715979	$(1+2*(3^4-5^6*7))^*(-8-9)$	4115133	$(1+234*(5^6+7)/8)^*9)$
3716299	$-1-2+34*(5^6*7-8^*9)$	4169904	$(1+2)*(-34+(5^6-7)^*89)$
3718325	$(1+2*(3^4-5^6*7))^*(-8-9)$	4169982	$-12-3*(4-(5^6-7)^*89)$
3719141	$(-1+2*(3^4+5^6*7))^*(8+9)$	4169997	$1+2-3*(4-(5^6-7)^*89)$
3719175	$(1+2*(3^4+5^6*7))^*(8+9)$	4170015	$-1-2+3*(4+(5^6-7)^*89)$
3721521	$(1+2*(3^4+5^6*7))^*(8+9)$	4170019	$-1+2+3*(4+(5^6-7)^*89)$
3721773	$-1-2+34*(5^6*7+89)$	4170020	$1^2+3*(4+(5^6-7)^*89)$
3721774	$-1^2+34*(5^6*7+89)$	4170021	$1+2+3*(4+(5^6-7)^*89)$
3721775	$1-2+34*(5^6*7+89)$	4170030	$12+3*(4+(5^6-7)^*89)$
3721777	$1^2+34*(5^6*7+89)$	4170108	$(1+2)*(34+(5^6-7)^*89)$
3721778	$1^2+34*(5^6*7+89)$	4173642	$(1+2)*(-34+(5^6+7)^*89)$
3721779	$1+2+34*(5^6*7+89)$	4173720	$-12-3*(4-(5^6+7)^*89)$
3738011	$(-1+2*(3^4+5^6)^*7)^*(8+9)$	4173753	$-1-2+3*(4+(5^6+7)^*89)$
3738045	$(1+2*(3^4+5^6)^*7)^*(8+9)$	4173768	$12+3*(4+(5^6+7)^*89)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
4173846	$(1+2)^*(34+(5^6+7)^*89)$	5046003	$(1+2^*(3^4*5+6^7-8))^*9$
4188456	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-4-5)^*6^7+8^9)$	5046273	$(-1+2^*(3^4*5+6^7+8))^*9$
4188621	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-4-5)^*6^7+8^9)$	5046291	$(1+2^*(3^4*5+6^7+8))^*9$
4188669	$(1+2)^*((3^4-4-5)^*6^7+8-9)$	5087628	$12^*3^*(-4+(5^6+78)^*9)$
4188675	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-4-5)^*6^7+8-9)$	5087916	$12^*3^*(4+(5^6+78)^*9)$
4188723	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-4-5)^*6^7-8-9)$	5124964	$-12^*3-4^*5^6*(7-89)$
4188888	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-4-5)^*6^7-8^*9)$	5124985	$-12-3-4^*5^6*(7-89)$
4209192	$(1+2)^*((3^4-4+5)^*6^7-8^*9)$	5125015	$12+3-4^*5^6*(7-89)$
4209357	$(1+2)^*((3^4-4+5)^*6^7-8-9)$	5140597	$(1-2^3)^*(4-5^6*(7^*8-9))$
4209405	$(1+2)^*((3^4-4+5)^*6^7+8-9)$	5140653	$(-1+2^3)^*(4+5^6*(7^*8-9))$
4209411	$(1+2)^*((3^4-4+5)^*6^7+8+9)$	5245692	$-12^*(3-4^*(5^6*7-89))$
4209459	$(1+2)^*((3^4-4+5)^*6^7+8+9)$	5245764	$12^*(3+4^*(5^6*7-89))$
4209624	$(1+2)^*((3^4-4+5)^*6^7+8^*9)$	5248650	$(1+2/3)/(4/(5^*(6^7-8)^*9))$
4214520	$(1+2/3)^*((4^5+6^7+8)^*9)$	5248896	$-12^*(3-4^*5^6*7+89)$
4217283	$(1+2^*(3^4-5^6*(7+8)))^*-9$	5249875	$-12^*(3-4^*5^6*7)-89$
4217301	$(1-2^*(3^4-5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	5250780	$-12^*(3-4^*(5^6*7+8+9))$
4218633	$(1-2^*(3+4-5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	5251032	$-12^*(3-4^*5^6*7-89)$
4218777	$(1-2^*(3-4-5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	5254236	$-12^*(3-4^*(5^6*7+89))$
4218867	$(-1+2^*(3+4+5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	5254308	$12^*(3+4^*(5^6*7+89))$
4220199	$(-1+2^*(3^4+5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	5390509	$-1+23^*(4+5^6*(7+8)-9)$
4220217	$(1+2^*(3^4+5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	5390644	$-1+(2+3)^*(4+5^6*(78-9))$
4240611	$(-1+2^*(3^4+5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	5390923	$-1+23^*(4+5^6*(7+8)+9)$
4240629	$(1+2^*(3^4+5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	5390925	$1+23^*(4+5^6*(7+8)+9)$
4499805	$(1+2)^*((3^4/5^6-6-7)^*8-9)$	5404488	$(-1-2^3)^*(4-5/(6/(7^8-9)))$
4499859	$(1+2)^*((3^4/5^6-6-7)^*8+9)$	5404497	$(1+2^3)^*(4+5/(6/(7^8-9)))$
4499898	$(1+2)^*(-34+5^6*(7+89))$	5484358	$1/2^*(-34+5^6*78^*9)$
4500013	$-1+2+3^*(4+5^6*(7+89))$	5484392	$1/2^*(34+5^6*78^*9)$
4500014	$1^*2+3^*(4+5^6*(7+89))$	5539625	$(1/-23+4)^*5^*(6^7+89)$
4500015	$1+2+3^*(4+5^6*(7+89))$	5558280	$-12^3+4^*(5^6-7)^*89$
4500102	$(1+2)^*(34+5^6*(7+89))$	5561736	$12^3+4^*(5^6-7)^*89$
4500141	$(1+2)^*((3^4/5^6-6+7)^*8-9)$	5563264	$-12^3+4^*(5^6+7)^*89$
4500195	$(1+2)^*((3^4/5^6-6+7)^*8+9)$	5566720	$12^3+4^*(5^6+7)^*89$
4501875	$(1+2)/(3+4)^5*(6+7-8-9)$	5577882	$(1+2)^*(-3^4+5^6*7^*(8+9))$
4536393	$-12+3^4/5^*(6^7+89)$	5577930	$(1+2)^*(3-(4-5^6*7)^*(8+9))$
4536417	$12+3^4/5^*(6^7+89)$	5578089	$(1+2)^*(3^*-4+5^6*7^*(8+9))$
4593405	$(-1+(2/3+4)^*(5^6*7-8))^*9$	5578113	$(1-2)^*3^*(4-5^6*7^*(8+9))$
4593423	$(1+(2/3+4)^*(5^6*7-8))^*9$	5578137	$1^*2^*3^*(4+5^6*7^*(8+9))$
4727673	$(1+2^*(3^4-5)^*(6^7-8))/9$	5578161	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6*7^*(8+9))$
4727943	$(-1+2^*(3^4-5)^*(6^7+8))/9$	5578320	$(1+2)^*(-3+(4+5^6*7)^*(8+9))$
4830119	$(1+2/3^4-4^*5^6*7)^*89$	5578338	$(1+2)^*(3+(4+5^6*7)^*(8+9))$
4867364	$1/(2/(-3+(4+5^6*7)^*89))$	5578368	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6*7^*(8+9))$
4873236	$-12^3+4^*(5^6*78-9)$	5622291	$(1+(2+3)^*(4-(5^6-7)^*8))^*-9$
4873308	$-12^3+4^*(5^6*78+9)$	5622309	$(1-(2+3)^*(4-(5^6-7)^*8))^*9$
4874856	$12^*3^*(-4+5^6*78/9)$	5622651	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4+(5^6-7)^*8))^*9$
4874928	$-12^*3+4^*(5^6*78-9)$	5622669	$(1+(2+3)^*(4+(5^6-7)^*8))^*9$
4874941	$-1^*23+4^*(5^6*78-9)$	5627331	$(1+(2+3)^*(4-(5^6+7)^*8))^*-9$
4874942	$1-23+4^*(5^6*78-9)$	5627349	$(1-(2+3)^*(4-(5^6+7)^*8))^*9$
4874949	$-12-3+4^*(5^6*78-9)$	5627691	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4+(5^6+7)^*8))^*9$
4874979	$12+3+4^*(5^6*78-9)$	5627709	$(1+(2+3)^*(4+(5^6+7)^*8))^*9$
4875021	$-12-3+4^*(5^6*78+9)$	5661375	$(1/23+4)^*(5^*(6^7+89))$
4875051	$12+3+4^*(5^6*78+9)$	5775313	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5^6)^*(7^*8-9)$
4875058	$-1+23+4^*(5^6*78+9)$	5775407	$(1+(2^3)^4*5^6)^*(7^*8-9)$
4875059	$1^*23+4^*(5^6*78+9)$	5810607	$(1+(2^3)^4-5^6)^*(7^*8)^*-9$
4875072	$12^*3+4^*(5^6*78+9)$	5810625	$(1-(2^3)^4-5^6)^*(7^*8)^*9$
4875144	$12^*3^*(4+5^6*78/9)$	5858160	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5-6+7-8)^9$
4876692	$12^3+4^*(5^6*78-9)$	5859105	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-5^6(-6+7+8)+9)$
4876764	$12^3+4^*(5^6*78+9)$	5859150	$(1+2^*3^4)^*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$
4921326	$(1+(2+3)^*(4-5^6*7+8))^*-9$	5859159	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-5^6(-6+7+8)-9)$
4921506	$(1+(2-3-4)^*(5^6*7-8))^*-9$	5859591	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6(-6+7+8)-9)$
4921524	$(1-(2-3-4)^*(5^6*7-8))^*9$	5859600	$(1+2^*3^4)^*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$
4921704	$(1+(2+3)^*(4+5^6*7-8))^*9$	5859645	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6(-6+7+8)+9)$
4922046	$(1+(2+3)^*(4-5^6*7-8))^*-9$	5860590	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5+(6+7-8)^9)$
4922226	$(1+(2-3-4)^*(5^6*7+8))^*-9$	5905593	$(1+2^*3^*(4-5^6*7+8))^*-9$
4922244	$(1-(2-3-4)^*(5^6*7+8))^*9$	5905611	$(1-2^*3^*(4-5^6*7+8))^*9$
4922406	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4+5^6*7+8))^*9$	5905881	$(1+2^*(3^*(4-5^6*7+8)))^*-9$
4922424	$(1+(2+3)^*(4+5^6*7+8))^*9$	5905899	$(1-2^*(3^*(4-5^6*7+8)))^*9$
4942629	$(1+2/3^4-4^*5^6*78)^*9$	5906025	$(-1+2^*3^*(4+5^6*7-8))^*9$
5031405	$(-1-2^*(3^4*5-6^7+8))^*9$	5906043	$(1+2^*3^*(4+5^6*7-8))^*9$
5031423	$(1-2^*(3^4*5-6^7+8))^*9$	5906169	$(1+2^*(3^*(4-5^6*7-8)))^*-9$
5031693	$(-1-2^*(3^4*5-6^7-8))^*9$	5906187	$(1-2^*(3^*(4-5^6*7-8)))^*9$
5031711	$(1-2^*(3^4*5-6^7-8))^*9$	5906313	$(-1+2^*(3^*(4+5^6*7-8)))^*9$
5045985	$(-1+2^*(3^4*5+6^7-8))^*9$	5906331	$(1+2^*(3^*(4+5^6*7-8)))^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
5906457	$(1+2^3*(4-5^6*7-8))^*-9$	6758460	$12*(3+(4^5*5^6+78)^*9)$
5906475	$(1-2^3*(4-5^6*7-8))^*9$	6783660	$-12*(3-4*(5^6+78)^*9)$
5906601	$(-1+2^3*(3*(4+5^6*7)+8))^*9$	6783732	$12*(3+4*(5^6+78)^*9)$
5906619	$(1+2^3*(3*(4+5^6*7)+8))^*9$	6796856	$1-(2+3)*(4-5^6*(78+9))$
5906889	$(-1+2^3*(4+5^6*7+8))^*9$	6796894	$-1+(2+3)*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
5906907	$(1+2^3*(4+5^6*7+8))^*9$	6796896	$1+(2+3)*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
5999985	$-12-3+4^5*5^6*(7+89)$	6890093	$(1-2^3)*(4-(5^6*7-8)^*9)$
6000015	$12+3+4^5*5^6*(7+89)$	6890149	$(-1+2^3)*(4+(5^6*7-8)^*9)$
6049728	$(-1+(2/3)^{-4*5})/(6^{\wedge}-7/(8/9))$	6891101	$(1-2^3)*(4-(5^6*7+8)^*9)$
6054912	$(1+(2/3+4)^5)/(6^{\wedge}-7/(8/9))$	6891157	$(-1+2^3)*(4+(5^6*7+8)^*9)$
6093749	$-1+234^5*5^6*(7+8)/9$	6949991	$1-(2+3)*(4-(5^6-7)^*89)$
6093751	$1+234^5*5^6*(7+8)/9$	6950029	$-1+(2+3)*(4+(5^6-7)^*89)$
6106547	$1-23*(4-(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	6950031	$1+(2+3)*(4+(5^6-7)^*89)$
6106729	$-1+23*(4+(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	6956259	$-1+(2+3)*(4+(5^6+7)^*89)$
6106730	$1^*23*(4+(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	7065255	$(-1+(2^3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^*7^*8+9)$
6106731	$1+23*(4+(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	7065945	$(1+(2^3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^*7^*8+9)$
6112203	$-1+23*(4+(5^6+7)^*(8+9))$	7085625	$(1+(2^3)^{\wedge}4*(5^6-7^*8))/9$
6124713	$(1-2^3)*((4-5^6*7)^*8+9)$	7109347	$(1-2^3)*(4+5^6*(7-8)^*9)$
6124839	$(1-2^3)*((4-5^6*7)^*8-9)$	7109403	$(1-2^3)*(-4+5^6*(7-8)^*9)$
6124909	$(1-2^3)*(4-5^6*7^*8+9)$	7110713	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^4))*(5^6-7/8)/9$
6124965	$(-1+2^3)*(4+5^6*7^*8-9)$	7312507	$1+2^3*(3*(4+5^6*78)-9)$
6125035	$(1-2^3)*(4-5^6*7^*8-9)$	7322162	$(-1+2^34)*(5^6*7-89)$
6125091	$(-1+2^3)*(4+5^6*7^*8+9)$	7334088	$(-1+2^34)*(5^6*7+89)$
6125161	$(-1+2^3)*((4+5^6*7)^*8-9)$	7392660	$12*(3-4/5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+89)$
6125287	$(-1+2^3)*((4+5^6*7)^*8+9)$	7431447	$-1+2^34*(5^6*7-89)$
6164022	$-1/2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^6*789)$	7431449	$1+2^34*(5^6*7-89)$
6164059	$-1/2*(3+4-5^6*789)$	7438027	$1+2^3*(34*(5^6*7+8)-9)$
6164062	$1/2*(3-4+5^6*789)$	7443551	$-1+2^34*(5^6*7+89)$
6164063	$-1/2*(3-4-5^6*789)$	7443553	$1+2^34*(5^6*7+89)$
6164066	$1/2*(3+4+5^6*789)$	7446519	$(-1+(2^3)^{\wedge}4*(5^6*7-8))^*9$
6164103	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^6*789)$	7446537	$(1+(2^3)^{\wedge}4*(5^6*7-8))^*9$
6266871	$(-1+(2^3)^{\wedge}4*5*(6^*7-8))^*9$	7499981	$1-(2+3)*(4-5^6*(7+89))$
6266889	$(1+(2^3)^{\wedge}4*5*(6^*7-8))^*9$	7500019	$-1+(2+3)*(4+5^6*(7+89))$
6377188	$12*(3^{\wedge}(4^5-6)-78)/9$	7500021	$1+(2+3)*(4+5^6*(7+89))$
6377396	$12*(3^{\wedge}(4^5-6)+78)/9$	7540734	$(1+2^34)*(5^6*7-89)$
6406231	$1-(2+3)*(4+5^6*(7-89))$	7553016	$(1+2^34)*(5^6*7+89)$
6499964	$-12*(3-4^5*5^6*78/9)$	7603032	$-12*(3+(4^5*5^6-7^{\wedge}8)/9)$
6500036	$12*(3+4^5*5^6*78/9)$	7603104	$12*(3-(4^5*5^6-7^{\wedge}8)/9)$
6561165	$(12+3)*(4^5*5^6*7-89)$	7686584	$12*(3^{\wedge}4+5^6+7^{\wedge}8)/9$
6563835	$(12+3)*(4^5*5^6*7+89)$	7781679	$(1+(2^3)^{\wedge}4-5^6*7^*8)^*-9$
6696633	$(-1+(2^3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^*7^*8-9)$	7781697	$(1-(2^3)^{\wedge}4-5^6*7^*8)^*9$
6697287	$(1+(2^3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^*7^*8-9)$	7858143	$(1+(234-5^6*7^*8)^*-9)$
6708717	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$	7858161	$(1-(234-5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6708771	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	7865775	$(1+(2^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^6*7^*8)^*-9)$
6716340	$12*(3+4*(5^6-78)^*9)$	7865793	$(1-(2^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6716373	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$	7869015	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4-5^6*7^*8)^*-9)$
6716427	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	7869033	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4-5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6716613	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$	7869303	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4+5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6716667	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	7869321	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4+5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6717222	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$	7871444	$(1-2^3)*(4-(5^6-7)^*8^*9)$
6717276	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	7871500	$(-1+2^3)*(4+(5^6-7)^*8^*9)$
6719652	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7^*8-9)$	7872893	$-1-(234-5^6*7^*8)^*9$
6719706	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7^*8+9)$	7872895	$1-(234-5^6*7^*8)^*9$
6720261	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	7873263	$(1+(2^3*4-5^6*7^*8)^*-9)$
6720315	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$	7873281	$(1-(2^3*4-5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6720501	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	7874289	$(1-(2^3+4-5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6720555	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$	7874799	$(1+(2/(3/4)-5^6*7^*8)^*-9)$
6728157	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	7874817	$(1-2/(3/4)-5^6*7^*8)^*9$
6728211	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$	7875183	$(-1+(2/(3/4)+5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6741540	$12*(-3+(4^5*5^6-78)^*9)$	7875201	$(1+(2/(3/4)+5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6743484	$-12*(3-4*(5^6-7-8)^*9)$	7875711	$(-1+(2^3+4+5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6746751	$(1+2^3*(4-(5^6-7)^*8))^*-9$	7876719	$(-1+(2^3*4+5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6746769	$(1-2^3*(4-(5^6-7)^*8))^*9$	7876737	$(1+(2^3*4+5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6747183	$(-1+2^3*(4+(5^6-7)^*8))^*9$	7877105	$-1+(234+5^6*7^*8)^*9$
6747201	$(1+2^3*(4+(5^6-7)^*8))^*9$	7877107	$1+(234+5^6*7^*8)^*9$
6747804	$12*(-3+(4*(5^6-7)+8)^*9)$	7878500	$(1-2^3)*(4-(5^6+7)^*8^*9)$
6750342	$-12*(3-4*(5^6+7/8)^*9)$	7878556	$(-1+2^3)*(4+(5^6+7)^*8^*9)$
6752799	$(1+2^3*(4-(5^6+7)^*8))^*-9$	7880679	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4-5^6*7^*8)^*-9)$
6752817	$(1-2^3*(4-(5^6+7)^*8))^*9$	7880697	$(1-(2-3^{\wedge}4-5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6753231	$(-1+2^3*(4+(5^6+7)^*8))^*9$	7880967	$(-1+(2+3^{\wedge}4+5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6753249	$(1+2^3*(4+(5^6+7)^*8))^*9$	7880985	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4+5^6*7^*8)^*9)$
6758388	$12*(-3+(4^5*5^6+78)^*9)$	7884207	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6*7^*8)^*9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
7884225	$(1+(2^{2^3+4})+5^{6^7})^*8)^*9$	9001071	$(1+2^*(3+(4/5^{6^7}-6+7)^*8))^*9$
7891839	$(-1+(234+5^{6^7})^*8)^*9$	9003735	$(1+2^{2^3}*(4-(5^{6^7})^*8))^*-9$
7891857	$(1+(234+5^{6^7})^*8)^*9$	9003753	$(1-2^{2^3}*(4-(5^{6^7})^*8))^*9$
7896705	$(12+3^{4/5})^*(6^{6^7+89})$	9003969	$(1+2^*(3-4^*(5^{6^7})^*8))^*-9$
7915671	$(1+(2-(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*7)^*8)^*-9$	9003987	$(1-2^*(3-4^*(5^{6^7})^*8))^*9$
7915689	$(1-(2-(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*7)^*8)^*9$	9004077	$(-1+2^*(3+4^*(5^{6^7})^*8))^*9$
7915959	$(-1+(2+(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*7)^*8)^*9$	9004095	$(1+2^*(3+4^*(5^{6^7})^*8))^*9$
7915977	$(1+(2+(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*7)^*8)^*9$	9004311	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(4+(5^{6^7})^*8))^*9$
7929480	$(1+2/3+4)^*5^*(6^{6^7-8^9})$	9004329	$(1+2^{2^3}*(4+(5^{6^7})^*8))^*9$
7933560	$(1+(2/3+4))^*(5^*(6^{6^7+8^9}))$	9027909	$(1+2)^*(3^{4+5}*(6^{6^7/8-9}))$
7964775	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(3^4))^*((5^{6^7+7})/8-9)$	9027963	$(1+2)^*(3^{4+5}*(6^{6^7/8+9}))$
7968303	$(1-((2^3)^{4+5^{6^7}})^*8)^*-9$	9071010	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(3^4))^*(5^{6^7/7-8-9})$
7968321	$(1+((2^3)^{4+5^{6^7}})^*8)^*9$	9136530	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(3^4))^*(5^{6^7/7+8-9})$
7968441	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(5^{6^7}*(7+8)-9))$	9144265	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(3^4))^*(5^{6^7/7+8/9})$
7968665	$(1+2^{2^3}*(3^4))^*((5^{6^7+7})/8-9)$	9144720	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(3^4))^*(5^{6^7/7-8+9})$
7969053	$(-1-2+3^{4^*}(5^{6^7}*(7+8)+9))$	9172566	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(3^4))^*(5^{6^7/7-8+9})$
7969059	$1+2+3^{4^*}(5^{6^7}*(7+8)+9)$	9210240	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(3^4))^*(5^{6^7/7+8+9})$
7978149	$(1+2)^*((3^{4-5})^*6^{6^7/8-9})$	9215991	$(-1+(2^{2^3})^{4^*}5^*(6^{7+8}))^*9$
7978203	$(1+2)^*((3^{4-5})^*6^{6^7/8+9})$	9216009	$(1+(2^{2^3})^{4^*}5^*(6^{7+8}))^*9$
7987135	$(-1+(2^{2^3})^{4^*}5^*(6^{7+8+9}))$	9224047	$(-1+(2-3^{4-4^*}5^*6^{6^7}))^*(8+9)$
7987265	$(1+(2^{2^3})^{4^*}5^*(6^{7+8+9}))$	9224081	$(1+(2-3^{4-4^*}5^*6^{6^7}))^*(8+9)$
8036343	$(-1+(2^{2^3})^{4^*}5^*(6^{7+8}))^*9$	9296518	$(1+(2+3)^*(4-5^{6^7}))^*(-8-9)$
8036361	$(1+(2^{2^3})^{4^*}5^*(6^{7+8}))^*9$	9296552	$(1-(2+3)^*(4-5^{6^7}))^*(8+9)$
8038485	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(3^4))^*((5^{6^7+7})/8+9)$	9297198	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4+5^{6^7}))^*(8+9)$
8042411	$(1+2^{2^3}*(3^4))^*((5^{6^7+7})/8+9)$	9297232	$(1+(2+3)^*(4+5^{6^7}))^*(8+9)$
8156275	$1+2^{2^3}*(4+5^{6^7}*(7+8+9))$	9349829	$(1+2^{2^3}*(3^4/5))^*(6^{6^7+8-9})$
8340037	$1+2^{2^3}*(4+(5^{6^7-7})^*89)$	9435465	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(3^4))^*(5^{6^7/7+8^9})$
8450180	$(-1-(23^{4-5^{6^7}+8}))^*9$	9504037	$(-1-2^*(3^{4^*}5-6^{6^7}))^*(8+9)$
8450182	$1-(23^{4-5^{6^7}+8})^*9$	9504071	$(1-2^*(3^{4^*}5-6^{6^7}))^*(8+9)$
8501814	$(-1-2)^*(3^{4^*}(5-6^{6^7/8})+9)$	9531577	$(-1+2^*(3^{4^*}5+6^{6^7}))^*(8+9)$
8501868	$(-1-2)^*(3^{4^*}(5-6^{6^7/8})-9)$	9531611	$(1+2^*(3^{4^*}5+6^{6^7}))^*(8+9)$
8504244	$(1+2)^*(3^{4^*}(5+6^{6^7/8})-9)$	9623042	$(-1+2^3)^*(4^*5^{6^7-89})$
8504298	$(1+2)^*(3^{4^*}(5+6^{6^7/8})+9)$	9682844	$(12+(3^{4-5^{6^7}})^*7)^*-89$
8531175	$(-12+(3+4)^*(5^{6^7}*(7+8-9)))$	9683900	$(-12-(3^{4-5^{6^7}})^*7^*89)$
8531199	$12+(3+4)^*(5^{6^7}*(7+8-9))$	9683924	$12-(3^{4-5^{6^7}})^*7^*89$
8531301	$(-12+(3+4)^*(5^{6^7}*(7+8+9)))$	9684980	$(12-(3^{4-5^{6^7}})^*7)^*89$
8531325	$12+(3+4)^*(5^{6^7}*(7+8+9))$	9707441	$(-1+(2^{2^3})^{4^*}5^*(6^{7+8^9}))$
8624907	$(-1-2^3*(4-5^{6^7}*(7+8+9)))$	9707599	$(1+(2^{2^3})^{4^*}5^*(6^{7+8^9}))$
8624909	$1-2^3*(4-5^{6^7}*(7+8+9))$	9727154	$(-12-(3^{4-5^{6^7}})^*89)$
8624967	$(-1-2^{2^3}*(4-5^{6^7}*(78-9)))$	9727178	$12-(3^{4-5^{6^7}})^*89$
8624969	$1-2^{2^3}*(4-5^{6^7}*(78-9))$	9731346	$(-1-2-(3^{4-5^{6^7}})^*89)$
8625031	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(4+5^{6^7}*(78-9)))$	9731347	$1^*-2-(3^{4-5^{6^7}})^*89$
8625033	$1+2^{2^3}*(4+5^{6^7}*(78-9))$	9731351	$1^*2-(3^{4-5^{6^7}})^*89$
8625091	$(-1+2^3*(4+5^{6^7}*(7+8+9)))$	9731352	$1+2-(3^{4-5^{6^7}})^*89$
8625092	$1^*2^3*(4+5^{6^7}*(7+8+9))$	9732291	$(-12^{2^3}-(4-5^{6^7})^*89)$
8625093	$1+2^3*(4+5^{6^7}*(7+8+9))$	9733003	$(-12^{2^3}+(4+5^{6^7})^*89)$
8640597	$(1-2^{2^3}*(4-5^{6^7}*(7+8^9)))$	9733983	$12^*-3-(4-5^{6^7})^*89$
8640653	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(4+5^{6^7}*(7+8^9)))$	9734055	$12^*3-(4-5^{6^7})^*89$
8789959	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(4/5)^*(6^{6^7+8-9}))$	9734274	$(-12+(3-4+5^{6^7})^*89)$
8845785	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(3^4))^*(5^{6^7/7-8^9})$	9734298	$12+(3-4+5^{6^7})^*89$
8846847	$(-1+((2^{2^3})^{4^*}5^*(6-7)^*8)^*9)$	9734452	$(-12-(3-4-5^{6^7})^*89)$
8846865	$(1+((2^{2^3})^{4^*}5^*(6-7)^*8)^*9)$	9734476	$12-(3-4-5^{6^7})^*89$
8847855	$(-1+((2^{2^3})^{4^*}5^*(6+7)^*8)^*9)$	9734695	$(-12^*3+(4+5^{6^7})^*89)$
8847873	$(1+((2^{2^3})^{4^*}5^*(6+7)^*8)^*9)$	9734767	$12^*3+(4+5^{6^7})^*89$
8852154	$(-12+3^{4^*}(5^{6^7}*(7+8-9)))$	9735747	$12^{2^3}-(4-5^{6^7})^*89$
8852178	$12+3^{4^*}(5^{6^7}*(7+8-9))$	9736459	$12^{2^3}+(4+5^{6^7})^*89$
8866572	$(-12+3^{4^*}(5^{6^7}*(7+8+9)))$	9737398	$(-1-2+(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*89)$
8866596	$12+3^{4^*}(5^{6^7}*(7+8+9))$	9737399	$(-1^*2+(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*89)$
8995671	$(1+2^{2^3}*(4-(5^{6^7-7})^*8))^*-9$	9737403	$1^*2+(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*89$
8995689	$(1-2^{2^3}*(4-(5^{6^7-7})^*8))^*9$	9737404	$1+2+(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*89$
8995905	$(1+2^*(3-4^*(5^{6^7-7})^*8))^*-9$	9741572	$(-12+(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*89)$
8995923	$(1-2^*(3-4^*(5^{6^7-7})^*8))^*9$	9741596	$12+(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*89$
8996013	$(-1+2^*(3+4^*(5^{6^7-7})^*8))^*9$	9749923	$1-2^*(3-4^*(5^{6^7-7})^*8)$
8996031	$(1+2^*(3+4^*(5^{6^7-7})^*8))^*9$	9749933	$(-1+2^*(3+4^*(5^{6^7-7})^*8))$
8996247	$(-1+2^{2^3}*(4+(5^{6^7-7})^*8))^*9$	9750067	$1-2^*(3-4^*(5^{6^7-7})^*8)$
8996265	$(1+2^{2^3}*(4+(5^{6^7-7})^*8))^*9$	9750077	$(-1+2^*(3+4^*(5^{6^7-7})^*8))$
8998929	$(1+2^*(3-(4/5^{6^7-6-7})^*8))^*-9$	9783770	$(-12+(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*7)^*89$
8998947	$(1-2^*(3-(4/5^{6^7-6-7})^*8))^*9$	9784826	$(-12+(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*7^*89)$
8999037	$(-1+2^*(3+(4/5^{6^7-6-7})^*8))^*9$	9784850	$12+(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*7^*89$
9000025	$1+2^{2^3}*(4+5^{6^7}*(7+8+9))$	9785906	$(12+(3^{4+5^{6^7}})^*7)^*89$
9000963	$(1-2^*(3-(4/5^{6^7-6+7})^*8))^*9$	9811567	$(-1+(2+3^{4-4^*}5^*6^{6^7}))^*(8+9)$
9001053	$(-1+2^*(3+(4/5^{6^7-6+7})^*8))^*9$	9811601	$(1+(2+3^{4-4^*}5^*6^{6^7}))^*(8+9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
9843021	$(-1+(2^*3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$	10968825	$12+(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
9843039	$(1+(2^*3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$	10968870	$12+(3^*4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
9844461	$(-1+(2^*3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$	10969037	$-1-(2-34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
9844479	$(1+(2^*3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$	10969039	$1-(2-34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
9945026	$(-1+23^*4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$	10969053	$-1-2+(34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
9961224	$(-1+23^*4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$	10969054	$-1^*2+(34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10054311	$-1+23^*4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$	10969055	$1-2+(34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10054313	$1+23^*4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$	10969057	$1^{\wedge}2+(34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10060452	$-1+23^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$	10969058	$1^*2+(34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10060453	$1^*23^*(4/5^{\wedge}-6*7-89)$	10969059	$1+2+(34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10060454	$1+23^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$	10969073	$-1+(2+34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10063030	$1+23^*(4^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)-9)$	10969075	$1+(2+34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10064548	$1+23^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$	10969361	$-1+(2^*34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10070687	$-1+23^*4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$	10969363	$1+(2^*34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10070689	$1+23^*4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$	10969467	$-12+(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10163598	$(1+23^*4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$	10969491	$12+(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10180152	$(1+23^*4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$	10969577	$-1+(23^*4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10198542	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6-7^*8^*9)$	10969579	$1+(23^*4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10199538	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(-6+7^*8^*9)$	10970442	$12^{\wedge}3-(4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10249967	$-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$	10970514	$12^{\wedge}3+(4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$
10249969	$1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$	11009544	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3+4^*5)/6)^*7^*8^*9$
10250031	$-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$	11010552	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4+5)/6)^*7^*8^*9$
10250033	$1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$	11025504	$(-12+(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9)$
10318887	$(-1+((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6)^*7^*8)^*9$	11025720	$(12+(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9)$
10318905	$(1+((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5-6)^*7^*8)^*9$	11119983	$-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
10324935	$(-1+((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+6)^*7^*8)^*9$	11119985	$1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
10324953	$(1+((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5+6)^*7^*8)^*9$	11120011	$1-2^*(3-4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
10376733	$1/(2+3)^*(456+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	11120047	$-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
10444290	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6+7^*8^*9)$	11129951	$-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$
10445310	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6+7^*8^*9)$	11129953	$1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$
10497864	$(1+23)^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$	11130015	$-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$
10499955	$(-1-2)^*((3-4/5^{\wedge}-6*7)^*8-9)$	11130017	$1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$
10499973	$1^{\wedge}2^*3*(4^*5^{\wedge}6*7^*8-9)$	11155825	$(1+2^*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7))^*(-8-9)$
10500027	$1^{\wedge}2^*3*(4^*5^{\wedge}6*7^*8+9)$	11155859	$(1-2^*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7))^*(8+9)$
10500045	$(1+2)^*((3+4/5^{\wedge}-6*7)^*8-9)$	11156641	$(-1+2^*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7))^*(8+9)$
10502136	$(1+23)^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$	11156675	$(1+2^*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7))^*(8+9)$
10546704	$(1-(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)))^*9$	11244951	$(-1+(2^*3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)^*9$
10547046	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)))^*9$	11244969	$(1+(2^*3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)^*9$
10761705	$(1+2^*(3^{\wedge}(4^*5-6)+7)/8)^*9$	11250396	$-12*(3-4*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)+9))$
10783106	$(-1-2)^*((3^*4)^{\wedge}5-6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$	11255031	$(-1+(2^*3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8)^*9$
10874967	$1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	11255049	$(1+(2^*3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8)^*9$
10874969	$1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	11333655	$(-12+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-78))^*9$
10875031	$-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	11333751	$-12+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9$
10875033	$1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	11333775	$12+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9$
10911735	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^*6+7)^*8)^*9$	11333871	$(12+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-78))^*9$
10911753	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^*6+7)^*8)^*9$	11427831	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*(6+7^*8))^*9$
10911780	$(12+(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)^*78)^*-9$	11427849	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*(6+7^*8))^*9$
10911996	$(12-(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)^*78)^*9$	11447379	$(-12+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+78))^*9$
10966986	$-12^{\wedge}3-(4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11447475	$-12+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9$
10967058	$-12^{\wedge}3+(4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11447499	$12+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9$
10967921	$-1-(23^*4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11447595	$(12+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+78))^*9$
10967923	$1-(23^*4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11470553	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
10968009	$-12-(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11479181	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
10968033	$12-(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11494642	$1+23^*(4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$
10968137	$-1-(2^*34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11520386	$(-1-2)^*(3^*4^{\wedge}5-6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
10968139	$1-(2^*34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11520511	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8+9)$
10968425	$-1-(2+34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11520513	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8+9)$
10968427	$1-(2+34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11520547	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8-9)$
10968441	$-1-2-(34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11520549	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8-9)$
10968442	$1^*-2-(34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11526518	$-12-3^*(4^{\wedge}5-6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
10968443	$1-2-(34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11526542	$12-3^*(4^{\wedge}5-6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
10968445	$1^{\wedge}2-(34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11528387	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
10968446	$1^*2-(34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11528567	$(-1-2)^*(345-6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
10968447	$1+2-(34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11528594	$(1-23+4)^*(56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$
10968461	$-1+(2-34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11530610	$(1-23+4)^*(-56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$
10968463	$1+(2-34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11530637	$(1+2)^*(345+6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
10968630	$-12-(3^*4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11530817	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
10968675	$-12-(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11532662	$-12+3^*(4^{\wedge}5+6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
10968691	$1^*-23-(4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11538655	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$
10968692	$1-23-(4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11538657	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$
10968808	$-1+23+(4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11538691	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8+9)$
10968809	$1^*23+(4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	11538693	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8+9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
11538818	$(1+2)^*(3^4 4^5+6^7 7^8/9)$	14624865	$12^*(-3^4+5^6*7^8)+9$
11580023	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^4 5+6^7 7^8/9)$	14624880	$12^*(3-4+5^6*7^8-9)$
11588651	$(1+2)^*(3^4(4+5)+6^7 7^8/9)$	14624904	$12+3^4*(5^6*7^8-9)$
11615760	$(1+(2-3^4(4^5-6)))/7)^*(-8-9)$	14624907	$12^*(-3-4+5^6*7^8)-9$
11615794	$(1-(2-3^4(4^5-6)))/7)^*(8+9)$	14624925	$12^*(-3-4+5^6*7^8)+9$
11813760	$12^*(-3+(4+5^6*7^8)^9)$	14624961	$-12+3^4*(4^5 5^6*7^8-9)$
11999967	$-1-2^4 3^*(4-5^6*(7+89))$	14624985	$12+3^4*(4^5 5^6*7^8-9)$
11999969	$1-2^4 3^*(4-5^6*(7+89))$	14625039	$12+3^4*(4^5 5^6*7^8+9)$
12000031	$-1+2^4 3^*(4+5^6*(7+89))$	14625075	$12^*(3+4+5^6*7^8)-9$
12000033	$1+2^4 3^*(4+5^6*(7+89))$	14625093	$12^*(3+4+5^6*7^8)+9$
12201975	$(1+(2^4 3)^4 4^*(5-6^7 7^8))^*-9$	14625096	$12^*(3-4+5^6*7^8+9)$
12201993	$(1-(2^4 3)^4 4^*(5-6^7 7^8))^*9$	14625099	$12^*(-3/4+5^6*7^8+9)$
12276098	$(1+2)^*(3^4)^4 5+6^7 7^8/9)$	14625120	$12+3^4*(5^6*7^8+9)$
12326829	$-1^*(2^3)^4 4+5^6*7^8$	14625135	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7^8)-9$
12371175	$(-1+((2^4 3)^4 4-5)^6 6^7 7^8)^*9$	14625153	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7^8)+9$
12371193	$(1+((2^4 3)^4 4-5)^6 6^7 7^8)^*9$	14625192	$12^*(3+4+5^6*7^8+9)$
12401415	$(-1+((2^4 3)^4 4+5)^6 6^7 7^8)^*9$	14625252	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7^8+9)$
12401433	$(1+((2^4 3)^4 4+5)^6 6^7 7^8)^*9$	14625864	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7^8-9)$
12570615	$(-1+(2^4 3)^4 4^*(5+6^7 7^8))^*9$	14625963	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7^8)-9$
12570633	$(1+(2^4 3)^4 4^*(5+6^7 7^8))^*9$	14625981	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7^8)+9$
12656025	$(1+2^3)^*(4-5^6*(7+8))^*-9$	14626080	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7^8+9)$
12656043	$(1-2^3)^*(4-5^6*(7+8))^*9$	14700708	$12^*((3^4+5^6)^6*7^8-9)$
12656457	$(-1+2^3)^*(4+5^6*(7+8))^*9$	14700924	$12^*((3^4+5^6)^6*7^8+9)$
12656475	$(1+2^3)^*(4+5^6*(7+8))^*9$	14765597	$(1-2^4)^*(4-5^6*(7+8)^9)$
12744252	$-12^*(3-4^*(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	14765653	$(-1+2^4)^*(4+5^6*(7+8)^9)$
12769140	$12^*(3^4+5^6)^*(6^7+89)$	14874439	$(1+2^4)^*(4-5^6*7^8)^*(-8-9)$
12895557	$-1-2^*(3^4 5+6-7^8 9)$	14874473	$(1-2^4)^*(4-5^6*7^8)^*(8+9)$
12895559	$1-2^*(3^4 5+6-7^8 9)$	14874881	$(-1-2^*(3-4/5^6-6^7))^*(8+9)$
12895581	$-1-2^*(3^4 5-6-7^8 9)$	14874915	$(1-2^*(3-4/5^6-6^7))^*(8+9)$
12895583	$1-2^*(3^4 5-6-7^8 9)$	14875085	$(-1+2^*(3+4/5^6-6^7))^*(8+9)$
12936528	$-12^*(3^4-5^6*(7^8-9))$	14875119	$(1+2^*(3+4/5^6-6^7))^*(8+9)$
12937416	$12^*(-3-4+5^6*(7^8-9))$	14875527	$(-1+2^4)^*(4+5^6*7^8)^*(8+9)$
12937584	$12^*(3+4+5^6*(7^8-9))$	14875561	$(1+2^4)^*(4+5^6*7^8)^*(8+9)$
12938472	$12^*(3^4+5^6*(7^8-9))$	15111576	$12^*(3^4*(5^6-7^8)-9)$
13015597	$(1-2^4)^*(4-5^6*7^8(8+9))$	15171473	$-1+(2^3 4^4-5^6*7^8)^*89$
13015653	$(-1+2^4)^*(4+5^6*7^8(8+9))$	15171475	$1+(2^3 4^4-5^6*7^8)^*89$
13338127	$(-1+2^3 4^4 5^6 6^7)/(8+9)$	15179628	$12^*(3^4*(5^6-7^8)-89)$
13487318	$-1+(2^3 4^4+5^6*7^8)^*9$	15181764	$12^*(3^4*(5^6-7^8)+89)$
13487320	$1+(2^3 4^4+5^6*7^8)^*9$	15193236	$12^*(3^4*(5^6+7^8)-89)$
13494348	$12^*(-3+(4+(5^6-7^8)^8)^*9)$	15195372	$12^*(3^4*(5^6+7^8)+89)$
13780233	$(-1+2^*(3+4)^*(5^6*7^8-8))^*9$	15263208	$12^*(3^4*(5^6+7^8)-9)$
13780251	$(1+2^*(3+4)^*(5^6*7^8-8))^*9$	15263424	$12^*(3^4*(5^6+7^8)+9)$
13782249	$(-1+2^*(3+4)^*(5^6*7^8+8))^*9$	15374028	$-12^*(3^4+5^6*(7^8-9))$
13782267	$(1+2^*(3+4)^*(5^6*7^8+8))^*9$	15374856	$-12^*(3^4+5^6*(7^8-9))$
13860855	$(-1+(2^4 3)^4 4^*(5+6^7 7^8)^*8)^*9$	15374916	$-12^*(3^4+5^6*(7^8-9))$
13860873	$(1+(2^4 3)^4 4^*(5+6^7 7^8)^*8)^*9$	15375084	$12^*(3+4-5^6*(7^8-9))$
13929857	$(1+(2^3 4^4 5^6-7)^*8)/9$	15375144	$12^*(3^4-5^6*(7^8-9))$
14070447	$(1+(2^4 3)^4 4^5)^*(678+9)$	15375972	$12^*(3^4-5^6*(7^8-9))$
14100087	$(1+2^4(3+4))^*(5^6*7^8-8)^*9$	15564966	$-1/(2/3-4)^*(5+6+7^8 9)$
14118663	$(1+2^4(3+4))^*(5^6*7^8+8)^*9$	15746796	$12^3*(4/5^6-6^7-89)$
14275521	$(-1-2)^*(3^4 5-6^7 7^8(8+9))$	15748263	$(1+2^*(3^4-5^6*7^8)^*8)^*-9$
14277951	$(1+2)^*(3^4 5+6^7 7^8(8+9))$	15748281	$(1-2^*(3^4-5^6*7^8)^*8)^*9$
14348550	$(1+2)^*(3^4(4^5-6)-7^*(8+9))$	15749361	$(1+2^*(3+(4-5^6*7^8)^*8))^*-9$
14349264	$(1+2)^*(3^4(4^5-6)+7^*(8+9))$	15749469	$(-1+2^*(3-(4-5^6*7^8)^*8))^*9$
14411737	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-5/(6/(7^8-9)))$	15749775	$(1+2^*(3^4-5^6*7^8)^*8)^*-9$
14411782	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-5/(6/(7^8+9)))$	15749793	$(1-2^*(3^4-5^6*7^8)^*8)^*9$
14411944	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-5/(6/(7^8-9)))$	15749847	$(-1+2^*(3-4+5^6*7^8)^*8)^*9$
14412061	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5/(6/(7^8+9)))$	15749865	$(1+2^*(3+4-5^6*7^8)^*8)^*-9$
14412136	$-1/(2/(3-45*(6+7^8 9)))$	15749883	$(1-2^*(3+4-5^6*7^8)^*8)^*9$
14412223	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5/(6/(7^8-9)))$	15749901	$(1-2^*(3/4-5^6*7^8)^*8)^*9$
14412268	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5/(6/(7^8+9)))$	15749973	$(-1+2^*(3-4+5^6*7^8)^*8)^*9$
14549076	$-12^*((3^4-5^6)^*7^8+9)$	15749992	$(1-2+3)^*(4+5^6*7^8 9)$
14549292	$-12^*((3^4-5^6)^*7^8-9)$	15750008	$(1-2+3)^*(4+5^6*7^8 9)$
14622703	$(-1+(2^4 3)^4 5^6 6^7)^*(8+9)$	15750027	$(1-2^*(3-4-5^6*7^8)^*8)^*9$
14622737	$(1+(2^4 3)^4 5^6 6^7)^*(8+9)$	15750099	$(-1+2^*(3/4+5^6*7^8)^*8)^*9$
14623920	$-12^*(3^4-5^6*7^8+9)$	15750117	$(-1+2^*(3+4+5^6*7^8)^*8)^*9$
14624019	$-12^*(3^4-5^6*7^8)-9$	15750135	$(1+2^*(3+4+5^6*7^8)^*8)^*9$
14624037	$-12^*(3^4-5^6*7^8)+9$	15750153	$(1-2^*(3-4-5^6*7^8)^*8)^*9$
14624136	$-12^*(3^4-5^6*7^8-9)$	15750207	$(-1+2^*(3^4+5^6*7^8)^*8)^*9$
14624748	$12^*(-3^4+5^6*7^8-9)$	15750225	$(1+2^*(3^4+5^6*7^8)^*8)^*9$
14624808	$12^*(-3-4+5^6*7^8-9)$	15750531	$(1-2^*(3-(4+5^6*7^8)^*8))^*9$
14624847	$12^*(-3^4+5^6*7^8)-9$	15750639	$(1+2^*(3+(4+5^6*7^8)^*8))^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
15751068	$12^*(3^4/5^{\wedge}6-6^*7+89)$	17297103	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8+9)$
15751737	$(1+2^*(3^4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*8)^*9$	17301666	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^*6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$
15820312	$1/-2+3^{\wedge}4/(5^*6/(7+8)^{\wedge}9)$	17301720	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^*6+7^{\wedge}8+9)$
15820313	$1/2+3^{\wedge}4/(5^*6/(7+8)^{\wedge}9)$	17306715	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3*(456+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
16116615	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$	17597783	$(-1+2/3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8^*9)$
16118937	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$	17606638	$(-1+2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8-9)$
16131063	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$	17609214	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*-7-8+9)$
16133385	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$	17609536	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*-7+8-9)$
16171815	$(12+3)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78-9))$	17612112	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*-7-8-9)$
16171935	$(12+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78-9))$	17620967	$(-1+2/3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8^*9)$
16282395	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6+789)$	17816389	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8^*9)$
16311528	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$	17825354	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8-9)$
16312356	$12^*(-3^*4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$	17827962	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8-9)$
16312416	$12^*(-3-4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$	17828288	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8+9)$
16312584	$12^*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$	17830896	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9)$
16312644	$12^*(3^*4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$	17839861	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8^*9)$
16313472	$12^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$	17999028	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7+89))$
16588791	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5^*6^*(7+8))^*9$	17999916	$12^*(-3-4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+89))$
16588809	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5^*6^*(7+8))^*9$	18000084	$12^*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+89))$
16679052	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	18000972	$12^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+89))$
16679880	$12^*(-3^*4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	18281055	$(12+3)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6^*78-9)$
16679940	$12^*(-3-4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	18281175	$(12+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*78-9)$
16680012	$-12+3^*4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89$	18281325	$(12+3)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6^*78+9)$
16680015	$12^*(-3/4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	18281445	$(12+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*78+9)$
16680036	$12+3^*4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89$	18984348	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6(6-7+8)-9)$
16680108	$12^*(3+4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	18984402	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6(6-7+8)+9)$
16680168	$12^*(3^*4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	19169271	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5^*(6+7)^*8)^*9$
16680996	$12^*(3^{\wedge}4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	19169289	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5^*(6+7)^*8)^*9$
16685643	$12+3^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89$	19218690	$(-12-3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89))$
16689357	$-12+3^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89$	19218810	$(12+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89))$
16689381	$12+3^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89$	19367583	$(1+((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*6)^*789$
16694004	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	19389675	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4+5)^*6)^*789$
16694832	$12^*(-3^*4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	19391253	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4+5)^*6)^*789$
16694892	$12^*(-3-4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	19462609	$(1+2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6^*7))^*-89$
16694964	$-12+3^*4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89$	19462697	$-1-2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
16694988	$12+3^*4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89$	19462699	$1-2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
16695060	$12^*(3+4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	19462787	$(1-2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6^*7))^*89$
16695120	$12^*(3^*4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	19468587	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$
16695948	$12^*(3^{\wedge}4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	19468589	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$
16740392	$1/2^*(3^{\wedge}(4^*5-6)^*7-8+9)$	19468681	$-1-2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$
16753620	$-12^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+89)$	19468683	$1-2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$
16755756	$-12^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7-89)$	19468737	$1-2^*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$
16836564	$12^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7-89)$	19468817	$-1+2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$
16838700	$12^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7+89)$	19468819	$1+2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$
16874703	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8)))^*-9$	19468911	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$
16874721	$(1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8)))^*9$	19468913	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$
16875279	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8)))^*9$	19469457	$1-2^*(3-(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89)$
16875297	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8)))^*9$	19474713	$(-1+2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6^*7))^*89$
16890532	$-1-23*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7^*8-9))$	19474801	$-1+2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
16890534	$1-23*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7^*8-9))$	19474803	$1+2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
16890716	$-1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7^*8-9))$	19474891	$(1+2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6^*7))^*89$
16890718	$1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7^*8-9))$	19686051	$(-1+(2+3)^*4*(5^{\wedge}6^*7-8))^*9$
17282091	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3*(-456+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	19686069	$(1+(2+3)^*4*(5^{\wedge}6^*7-8))^*9$
17287086	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*-5^*6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	19687131	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4/5^{\wedge}6^*7-8))^*9$
17287140	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*-5^*6+7^{\wedge}8+9)$	19687149	$(1+(2+3)^*(4/5^{\wedge}6^*7-8))^*9$
17291703	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(-5-6)+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	19687490	$(1/2-3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7^*8^*9)$
17291757	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(-5-6)+7^{\wedge}8+9)$	19687510	$(1/-2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7^*8^*9)$
17292828	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*-6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	19687851	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4/5^{\wedge}6^*7+8))^*9$
17292882	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*-6+7^{\wedge}8+9)$	19687869	$(1+(2+3)^*(4/5^{\wedge}6^*7+8))^*9$
17292890	$-1-(23+4)^*(56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	19688931	$(-1+(2+3)^*4*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+8))^*9$
17292891	$(1^*23+4)^*(-56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	19688949	$(1+(2+3)^*4*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+8))^*9$
17292892	$1-(23+4)^*(56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	19955799	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5^*6^*(78+9)$
17293143	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*-5-6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	20114535	$(-1+2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$
17293233	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*-5+6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	20117433	$(-1+2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$
17295573	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	20124702	$1-23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7^*8+9)$
17295663	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6+7^{\wedge}8+9)$	20125530	$1+23^*((4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*8-9)$
17295914	$-1+(23+4)^*(56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	20132567	$(-1+2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$
17295915	$(1^*23+4)^*(56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	20135465	$(-1+2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$
17295916	$1+(23+4)^*(56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	20364405	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$
17295924	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	20367339	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$
17295978	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8+9)$	20382661	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$
17297049	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	20385595	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
20390565	$(12+3)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	22780233	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4/5^{\wedge}6-7*8))^*9$
20390685	$(12+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	22780251	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4/5^{\wedge}6-7*8))^*9$
20849970	$(12+3)^*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$	22782249	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4/5^{\wedge}6-7*8))^*9$
20850090	$(12+3)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$	22782267	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4/5^{\wedge}6-7*8))^*9$
20868660	$(12+3)^*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$	22782699	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7+8))^*9$
20868780	$(12+3)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$	22782717	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7+8))^*9$
21268360	$-12+(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-89)$	22791303	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)-8))^*9$
21268384	$12+(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-89)$	22791321	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)-8))^*9$
21275035	$-12+(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7-89$	22791591	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)+8))^*9$
21275237	$12+(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+89$	22791609	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)+8))^*9$
21281888	$-12+(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+89)$	22803111	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7+8))^*9$
21281912	$12+(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+89)$	22803129	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7+8))^*9$
21874775	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7*8-9)$	22862889	$(-1+2/3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7*8))^*9$
21875225	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7*8+9)$	22862907	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7*8))^*9$
21936879	$(1+2*(34-5^{\wedge}6*78))^*-9$	22996560	$-12*3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)/9)$
21936887	$-1-2*(34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	22996848	$12*3*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)/9)$
21936889	$1-2*(34-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	23049484	$12*3*(-45*6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
21936897	$(1-2*(34-5^{\wedge}6*78))^*9$	23051140	$12*3*(-4*56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
21937337	$-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*78*9)$	23057044	$12*3*(-4-56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
21937339	$1-2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*78*9)$	23057187	$-1-(2+34)*(56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$
21937431	$-1-2*(34-5^{\wedge}6*78*9)$	23057189	$1-(2+34)*(56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$
21937487	$-1-2*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*78*9)$	23057332	$12*3*(4-56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
21937567	$-1+2*(34+5^{\wedge}6*78*9)$	23057368	$12*3*(-45-6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
21937569	$1+2*(34+5^{\wedge}6*78*9)$	23057800	$12*3*(-45+6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
21937661	$-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78*9)$	23059378	$12*(3*(4+5/6+7^{\wedge}8/9))$
21937663	$1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78*9)$	23060608	$12*3*(45-6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
21938103	$(-1+2*(34+5^{\wedge}6*78))^*9$	23061040	$12*3*(45+6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
21938111	$-1+2*(34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	23061076	$12*3*(-4+56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
21938113	$1+2*(34+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	23061219	$-1+(2+34)*(56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
21938121	$(1+2*(34+5^{\wedge}6*78))^*9$	23061221	$1+(2+34)*(56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
22020192	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*56)^*(7+89)$	23061364	$12*3*(4+56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
22265625	$(1+2)^*(3+4/5)^*(6+7-8)^{\wedge}9$	23067268	$12*3*(4*56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
22313280	$12*(-3+(4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*(8+9))$	23068924	$12*3*(45*6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
22489911	$(-1+(2+3)^*4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)^*9$	23121560	$12*3*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)/9)$
22489929	$(1+(2+3)^*4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)^*9$	23121848	$12*3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)/9)$
22497471	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4/5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)^*9$	23359282	$-1-23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-8*9))$
22497489	$(1+(2+3)^*(4/5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)^*9$	23359284	$1-23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-8*9))$
22499940	$(12+3)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	23359466	$-1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7*8+9))$
22500060	$(12+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	23359468	$1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7*8+9))$
22502511	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4/5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)^*9$	23623263	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
22502529	$(1+(2+3)^*(4/5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)^*9$	23623281	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
22510071	$(-1+(2+3)^*4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)*8)^*9$	23623983	$(1+(2+3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7))^*8)^*-9$
22510089	$(1+(2+3)^*4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)*8)^*9$	23624001	$(1-(2+3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7))^*8)^*9$
22642190	$1-23*(4-(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$	23624271	$(-1+(2-3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7))^*8)^*9$
22667190	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7+89)$	23624289	$(1+(2-3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7))^*8)^*9$
22667214	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7+89)$	23624559	$(1-2*3*(4/5^{\wedge}6-7*8))^*-9$
22668000	$-12+3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7-89)$	23624577	$(1+2*3*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
22668024	$12+3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7-89)$	23624847	$(-1+2*(3*4*5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
22674310	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)-89$	23624964	$(1+2)^*(3*-4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$
22674334	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)-89$	23624979	$(1+2)^*(-3-4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$
22674488	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)+89$	23624988	$(1-2)^*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$
22674512	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)+89$	23624997	$(1+2)^*(3-4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$
22675120	$-12+3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)-89$	23625003	$(1+2)^*(-3+4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$
22675144	$12+3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)-89$	23625012	$1^{\wedge}2*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$
22675298	$-12+3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)+89$	23625021	$(1+2)^*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$
22675322	$12+3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)+89$	23625036	$(1+2)^*(3*4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$
22681608	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7-89)$	23625153	$(1+2*(3*4*5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
22681632	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7-89)$	23625423	$(1-2*3*(4/5^{\wedge}6-7*8))^*-9$
22682418	$-12+3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7+89)$	23625441	$(1+2*3*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
22682442	$12+3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7+89)$	23625711	$(1+(2-3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7))^*8)^*-9$
22699593	$(-1+2/3^{\wedge}4-4*(5^{\wedge}6-7*8))^*9$	23625729	$(1-(2-3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7))^*8)^*9$
22699611	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}4-4*(5^{\wedge}6-7*8))^*9$	23625999	$(-1+(2+3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7))^*8)^*9$
22708215	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6)^*7*8)^*9$	23626017	$(1+(2+3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7))^*8)^*9$
22708233	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6)^*7*8)^*9$	23626719	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
22759371	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7-8))^*9$	23626737	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
22759389	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7-8))^*9$	23677039	$(1+(2/3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(-8-9)$
22770891	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)-8))^*9$	23677073	$(1-(2/3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$
22770909	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)-8))^*9$	23718662	$(1-23)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$
22771179	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)+8))^*9$	23718838	$(-1+23)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$
22771197	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)+8))^*9$	23912047	$(-1+(2/3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$
22779783	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7-8))^*9$	23912081	$(1+(2/3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$
22779801	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7-8))^*9$	24066830	$-12+(3^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-89)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
24066854	$12+(3^4+5)^*(6^7-89)$	25593516	$1*234*(5^6*7+8-9)$
24074395	$-12+(3^4+5)^*6^7-89$	25593517	$1+234*(5^6*7+8-9)$
24074419	$12+(3^4+5)^*6^7-89$	25593541	$-1+234*(5^6*7-8/9)$
24074573	$-12+(3^4+5)^*6^7+89$	25593542	$1*234*(5^6*7-8/9)$
24074597	$12+(3^4+5)^*6^7+89$	25593543	$1+234*(5^6*7-8/9)$
24082138	$-12+(3^4+5)^*(6^7+89)$	25593957	$-1+234*(5^6*7+8/9)$
24082162	$12+(3^4+5)^*(6^7+89)$	25593958	$1*234*(5^6*7+8/9)$
24394722	$(1+((2^3)^4-5)^*67)^*89$	25593959	$1+234*(5^6*7+8/9)$
24424359	$(-1+2^*(3+4+5)^*67)^*89$	25593983	$-1+234*(5^6*7-8+9)$
24424537	$(1+2^*(3+4+5)^*67)^*89$	25593984	$1*234*(5^6*7-8+9)$
24499937	$(-1+2^3)^*(4/5^6-6^*7^*8-9)$	25593985	$1+234*(5^6*7-8+9)$
24500063	$(-1+2^3)^*(4/5^6-6^*7^*8+9)$	25595612	$-1+234*(5^6*7+8)-9$
24656087	$-1-2*(3^4-5^6*789)$	25595614	$1+234*(5^6*7+8)-9$
24656088	$1*2*(-3^4+5^6*789)$	25595630	$-1+234*(5^6*7+8)+9$
24656089	$1-2*(3^4-5^6*789)$	25595632	$1+234*(5^6*7+8)+9$
24656225	$-1-2*(3^4-5^6*789)$	25597727	$-1+234*(5^6*7+8+9)$
24656227	$1-2*(3^4-5^6*789)$	25597728	$1*234*(5^6*7+8+9)$
24656235	$-1-2*(3+4-5^6*789)$	25597729	$1+234*(5^6*7+8+9)$
24656236	$1*2*(-3-4+5^6*789)$	25610597	$-1+234*(5^6*7+8^*9)$
24656237	$1-2*(3+4-5^6*789)$	25610599	$1+234*(5^6*7+8^*9)$
24656242	$(1^2-3)^*(4-5^6*789)$	25686205	$(1+234)*(5^6*7-8^*9)$
24656247	$-1+2*(3-4+5^6*789)$	25699130	$(1+234)*(5^6*7-8-9)$
24656248	$1*2*(3-4+5^6*789)$	25702890	$(1+234)*(5^6*7+8-9)$
24656252	$1*2*(-3+4+5^6*789)$	25703360	$(1+234)*(5^6*7-8+9)$
24656253	$1-2*(3-4-5^6*789)$	25707120	$(1+234)*(5^6*7+8+9)$
24656258	$(1-2+3)^*(4+5^6*789)$	25720045	$(1+234)*(5^6*7+8^*9)$
24656263	$-1+2*(3+4+5^6*789)$	25863317	$1-23*(4-(5^6-7)^*8^*9)$
24656264	$1*2*(3+4+5^6*789)$	25871309	$1/(2/(34-(5^6-7^8)^*9))$
24656265	$1+2*(3+4+5^6*789)$	25874904	$(1+23)^*(-4+5^6*(78-9))$
24656273	$-1+2*(3^4+5^6*789)$	25875096	$(1+23)*(4+5^6*(78-9))$
24656275	$1+2*(3^4+5^6*789)$	25886917	$1/2*((-3-4)^*5^6+7^8^*9)$
24656411	$-1+2*(3^4+5^6*789)$	25933798	$1/2*(3^4-5^6+7^8^*9)$
24656412	$1*2*(3^4+5^6*789)$	25938534	$1/2*(3-4^5+6+7^8^*9)$
24656413	$1+2*(3^4+5^6*789)$	25941378	$1/2*(3-456+7^8^*9)$
24796782	$-1-23*(4-5^6*(78-9))$	25941435	$1/2*(-345+6+7^8^*9)$
24796783	$1*23*(-4+5^6*(78-9))$	25941774	$1/2*(345-6+7^8^*9)$
24796784	$1-23*(4-5^6*(78-9))$	25941831	$1/2*(-3+456+7^8^*9)$
24796966	$-1+23*(4+5^6*(78-9))$	25942050	$1/2*(3^4*(5+6)+7^8^*9)$
24796967	$1*23*(4+5^6*(78-9))$	25949423	$1/2*(3^4+5^6+7^8^*9)$
24796968	$1+23*(4+5^6*(78-9))$	25972856	$1/2*(3+4^5+6+7^8^*9)$
24963291	$(1+((2^3)^4-5)^*678)^*9$	26011900	$1/(2/(-34+(5^6+7^8)^*9))$
25131879	$(-1-2*((3^4-4-5)^*6^7+8))^*9$	26031233	$(-1+(2+3^4)/5^6-6^*7)^*(8+9)$
25131897	$(1-2*((3^4-4-5)^*6^7+8))^*9$	26031267	$(1+(2+3^4)/5^6-6^*7)^*(8+9)$
25132167	$(-1-2*((3^4-4-5)^*6^7-8))^*9$	26574417	$1/2*(3^4*5^6+7^8^*9)$
25132185	$(1-2*((3^4-4-5)^*6^7-8))^*9$	26576154	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6*7-8)-9)$
25256295	$(-1+2*((3^4-4+5)^*6^7-8))^*9$	26576208	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6*7-8)+9)$
25256313	$(1+2*((3^4-4+5)^*6^7-8))^*9$	26580042	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6*7+8)-9)$
25256583	$(-1+2*((3^4-4+5)^*6^7+8))^*9$	26580096	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6*7+8)+9)$
25256601	$(1+2*((3^4-4+5)^*6^7+8))^*9$	26738766	$1/2*(3^4(4+5)^6+7^8^*9)$
25312490	$(1-2*3^4*5^6)^*(7-8-9)$	26812214	$(1-23)*(4-5^6*7+8+9)$
25312510	$(-1-2*3^4*5^6)^*(7-8-9)$	26812390	$(-1+23)*(4+5^6*78-9)$
25312896	$12*(-3+(4+5^6*(7+8))^*9)$	26812610	$(1-23)*(4-5^6*78-9)$
25467599	$(-1+234)*(5^6*7-8^*9)$	26812786	$(-1+23)*(4+5^6*78+9)$
25480414	$(-1+234)*(5^6*7-8-9)$	26987895	$(-1+2*3^4*(5^6-7)^*8)^*9$
25484142	$(-1+234)*(5^6*7+8-9)$	26987913	$(1+2*3^4*(5^6-7)^*8)^*9$
25484608	$(-1+234)*(5^6*7-8+9)$	26996967	$(-1+2*3^4*(4^5+6-7)^*8)^*9$
25488336	$(-1+234)*(5^6*7+8+9)$	26996985	$(1+2*3^4*(4^5+6-7)^*8)^*9$
25501151	$(-1+234)*(5^6*7+8^*9)$	26998983	$(1-2*(3^4/5^6-6-7)^*8)^*-9$
25508751	$-12-3^4*(5-6^7/8^*9)$	26999001	$(1+2*(3^4*5^6-7)^*8)^*9$
25508775	$12-3^4*(5-6^7/8^*9)$	26999487	$(-1+(2^3*3^4*5^6-7)^*8)^*9$
25509561	$-12+3^4*(5+6^7/8^*9)$	26999505	$(1+(2^3*3^4*5^6-7)^*8)^*9$
25509585	$12+3^4*(5+6^7/8^*9)$	27000495	$(-1+(2^3*3^4*5^6+7)^*8)^*9$
25576901	$-1+234*(5^6*7-8^*9)$	27000513	$(1+(2^3*3^4*5^6+7)^*8)^*9$
25576903	$1+234*(5^6*7-8^*9)$	27000999	$(1-2*(3^4/5^6-6+7)^*8)^*-9$
25589771	$-1+234*(5^6*7-8-9)$	27001017	$(1+2*(3^4*5^6+7)^*8)^*9$
25589772	$1*234*(5^6*7-8-9)$	27003015	$(-1+2*3^4*(4^5+6+7)^*8)^*9$
25589773	$1+234*(5^6*7-8-9)$	27003033	$(1+2*3^4*(4^5+6+7)^*8)^*9$
25591868	$-1+234*(5^6*7-8)-9$	27562486	$(1/2+3)*(-4+5^6*7^*8^*9)$
25591870	$1+234*(5^6*7-8)-9$	27562514	$(1/2+3)*(4+5^6*7^*8^*9)$
25591886	$-1+234*(5^6*7-8)+9$	28030950	$-1-23*(4-5^6*7+8+9)$
25591888	$1+234*(5^6*7-8)+9$	28030951	$1*23*(-4+5^6*78-9)$
25593515	$-1+234*(5^6*7+8-9)$	28030952	$1-23*(4-5^6*78+9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
28031134	$-1+23*(4+5^6*78-9)$	30388581	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6+7)*8-9)$
28031135	$1*23*(4+5^6*78-9)$	30388635	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6+7)*8+9)$
28031136	$1+23*(4+5^6*78-9)$	30579956	$(1-23)*(4-(5^6-7)*89)$
28031364	$-1-23*(4-5^6*78-9)$	30580132	$(-1+23)*(4+(5^6-7)*89)$
28031365	$1*23*(-4+5^6*78+9)$	30607368	$(1-23)*(4-(5^6+7)*89)$
28031366	$1-23*(4-5^6*78-9)$	30607544	$(-1+23)*(4+(5^6+7)*89)$
28031548	$-1+23*(4+5^6*78+9)$	30662236	$-12*(3+4*(5^6-7^8)/9)$
28031549	$1*23*(4+5^6*78+9)$	30662308	$12*(3-4*(5^6-7^8)/9)$
28031550	$1+23*(4+5^6*78+9)$	30689280	$(1+2)/((3^4)^{-5}/(6^7-8/9))$
28038758	$1/2*(3+4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8^9)$	30749904	$(-1-23)*(4+5^6*(7-89))$
28187412	$(1-23)*(4+5^6*(7-89))$	30750096	$(1+23)*(4-5^6*(7-89))$
28187588	$(1-23)*(-4+5^6*(7-89))$	31265532	$-1-23*(4-5^6*(78+9))$
28301247	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*5)*(6^{\wedge}7/8-9)$	31265533	$1*23*(-4+5^6*(78+9))$
28315809	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*5)*(6^{\wedge}7/8+9)$	31265534	$1-23*(4-5^6*(78+9))$
28371213	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*5)*(6^{\wedge}7/8-9)$	31265716	$-1+23*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
28385811	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*5)*(6^{\wedge}7/8+9)$	31265717	$1*23*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
28390532	$-1-23*(4-5^6*(7+8^9))$	31265718	$1+23*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
28390534	$1-23*(4-5^6*(7+8^9))$	31499415	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3-4/5^{\wedge}6-6^7)*8)^{-9}$
28390716	$-1+23*(4+5^6*(7+8^9))$	31499577	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3-4/5^{\wedge}6-6^7)*8)^9$
28390718	$1+23*(4+5^6*(7+8^9))$	31499631	$(1+(2+3-4/5^{\wedge}6-6^7)*8)^{-9}$
29109855	$(-1+234)*((5^6-7)*8-9)$	31499649	$(1-(2+3-4/5^{\wedge}6-6^7)*8)^9$
29114049	$(-1+234)*((5^6-7)*8+9)$	31499943	$(1+(2/3-4/5^{\wedge}6-6^7)*8)^{-9}$
29135951	$(-1+234)*((5^6+7)*8-9)$	31500057	$(1+(2/3+4/5^{\wedge}6-6^7)*8)^9$
29140145	$(-1+234)*((5^6+7)*8+9)$	31500351	$(-1+(2+3+4/5^{\wedge}6-6^7)*8)^9$
29200989	$(12+3*(4-5^6*7))^{\wedge}8-9$	31500369	$(1+(2+3+4/5^{\wedge}6-6^7)*8)^9$
29202045	$-12-3*(4-5^6*7)*89$	31500423	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3+4*5^6*7)*8)^9$
29202069	$12-3*(4-5^6*7)*89$	31500585	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3+4/5^{\wedge}6-6^7)*8)^9$
29203023	$(1+2)*(-34+5^6*7*89)$	31969953	$-1-23*(4-(5^6-7)*89)$
29203101	$-12-3*(4-5^6*7*89)$	31969954	$1*23*(-4+(5^6-7)*89)$
29203116	$1+2-3*(4-5^6*7*89)$	31969955	$1-23*(4-(5^6-7)*89)$
29203149	$12+3*(4+5^6*7*89)$	31970137	$-1+23*(4+(5^6-7)*89)$
29203227	$(1+2)*(34+5^6*7*89)$	31970138	$1*23*(4+(5^6-7)*89)$
29204181	$-12+3*(4+5^6*7*89)$	31970139	$1+23*(4+(5^6-7)*89)$
29204205	$12+3*(4+5^6*7*89)$	31998611	$-1-23*(4-(5^6+7)*89)$
29205261	$(12+3*(4+5^6*7))^{\wedge}89$	31998612	$1*23*(-4+(5^6+7)*89)$
29234789	$-1+234*((5^6-7)*8-9)$	31998613	$1-23*(4-(5^6+7)*89)$
29234790	$1*234*((5^6-7)*8-9)$	31998795	$-1+23*(4+(5^6+7)*89)$
29234791	$1+234*((5^6-7)*8-9)$	31998796	$1*23*(4+(5^6+7)*89)$
29239001	$-1+234*((5^6-7)*8+9)$	31998797	$1+23*(4+(5^6+7)*89)$
29239002	$1*234*((5^6-7)*8+9)$	32016384	$(1+2)*(3^4)^{\wedge}5*(6^7+8/9)$
29239003	$1+234*((5^6-7)*8+9)$	32624904	$(1+23)*(-4+5^6*(78+9))$
29249688	$(1+23)*(-4+5^6*78-9)$	32625096	$(1+23)*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
29249880	$(1+23)*(4+5^6*78-9)$	32906034	$(12+3*(4-5^6*78))^{\wedge}8-9$
29250120	$(1+23)*(-4+5^6*78+9)$	32906130	$-12-3*(4-5^6*78)^9$
29250312	$(1+23)*(4+5^6*78+9)$	32906148	$(1+2)*(-34+5^6*78^9)$
29260997	$-1+234*((5^6+7)*8-9)$	32906154	$12-3*(4-5^6*78)^9$
29260998	$1*234*((5^6+7)*8-9)$	32906226	$-12-3*(4-5^6*78^9)$
29260999	$1+234*((5^6+7)*8-9)$	32906274	$12+3*(4+5^6*78^9)$
29265209	$-1+234*((5^6+7)*8+9)$	32906346	$-12+3*(4+5^6*78)^9$
29265210	$1*234*((5^6+7)*8+9)$	32906352	$(1+2)*(34+5^6*78^9)$
29265211	$1+234*((5^6+7)*8+9)$	32906370	$12+3*(4+5^6*78)^9$
29359725	$(1+234)*((5^6-7)*8-9)$	32906466	$(12+3*(4+5^6*78))^{\wedge}9$
29363955	$(1+234)*((5^6-7)*8+9)$	32999912	$(1-23)*(4-5^6*(7+89))$
29386045	$(1+234)*((5^6+7)*8-9)$	33000088	$(-1+23)*(4+5^6*(7+89))$
29390275	$(1+234)*((5^6+7)*8+9)$	33359952	$(1+23)*(-4+(5^6-7)*89)$
29468657	$-1-23*(4+5^6*(7-89))$	33360144	$(1+23)*(4+(5^6-7)*89)$
29468658	$-1*23*(4+5^6*(7-89))$	33389856	$(1+23)*(-4+(5^6+7)*89)$
29468659	$1-23*(4+5^6*(7-89))$	33390048	$(1+23)*(4+(5^6+7)*89)$
29468841	$-1+23*(4-5^6*(7-89))$	33509349	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^6*7^8+9)$
29468842	$1*23*(4-5^6*(7-89))$	33509403	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^6*7^8-9)$
29468843	$1+23*(4-5^6*(7-89))$	33590349	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5^6*7^8)^9)$
29673216	$(1-(2/3-4)^5)/6^{\wedge}(-7+8-9)$	33590403	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5^6*7^8)^9)$
29906162	$(1-23)*(4-5^6*(78+9))$	33594237	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5^6*7^8)^9)$
29906338	$(-1+23)*(4+5^6*(78+9))$	33594291	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5^6*7^8)^9)$
29977245	$-1+234/5*(6+7^8/9)$	33675237	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-4+5)^6*7^8-9)$
29977246	$1*234/5*(6+7^8/9)$	33675291	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-4+5)^6*7^8+9)$
29977247	$1+234/5*(6+7^8/9)$	33908418	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^6*(6+7))/8)/9$
30231873	$(1+2)*(3^4*5-6/(7-8))^{\wedge}9$	34331808	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^6*(7+89)$
30234303	$(1+2)*(3^4*5-6/(7-8))^{\wedge}9$	34472433	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^6*(78+9)$
30235536	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4))*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$	34499907	$-1-23*(4-5^6*(7+89))$
30361365	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6-7)*8-9)$	34499908	$1*23*(-4+5^6*(7+89))$
30361419	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5^6-7)*8+9)$	34499909	$1-23*(4-5^6*(7+89))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
34500091	$-1+23*(4+5^6*(7+89))$	40252473	$(1-2*(3^4*5-6^7)*8)^9$
34500092	$1*23*(4+5^6*(7+89))$	40298391	$(-1-2*(3^4+5-6^7)*8)^9$
34500093	$1+23*(4+5^6*(7+89))$	40298409	$(1-2*(3^4+5-6^7)*8)^9$
34550558	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6*(7-89)$	40299831	$(-1-2*(3^4-5-6^7)*8)^9$
34640223	$-1+(23^4+5^6*7)^8*9$	40299849	$(1-2*(3^4-5-6^7)*8)^9$
34640225	$1+(23^4+5^6*7)^8*9$	40303485	$(-1-2*(3^4*5-6^7*8))^9$
34753683	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^6*(78-9)$	40303503	$(1-2*(3^4*5-6^7*8))^9$
35441183	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^{\wedge}((-6+78)/9)$	40318065	$(-1+2*(3^4*5+6^7*8))^9$
35690481	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)-(5^6+78)^9$	40318083	$(1+2*(3^4*5+6^7*8))^9$
35691885	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)-(5^6-78)^9$	40321719	$(-1+2*(3^4-5+6^7)*8)^9$
35971731	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)+(5^6-78)^9$	40321737	$(1+2*(3^4-5+6^7)*8)^9$
35973135	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)+(5^6+78)^9$	40323159	$(-1+2*(3^4+5+6^7)*8)^9$
35995959	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4/5^{\wedge}-6-7)^8)^9$	40323177	$(1+2*(3^4+5+6^7)*8)^9$
35995977	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4/5^{\wedge}-6-7)^8)^9$	40369095	$(-1+2*(3^4*5+6^7*8))^9$
36004023	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4/5^{\wedge}-6+7)^8)^9$	40369113	$(1+2*(3^4*5+6^7*8))^9$
36004041	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4/5^{\wedge}-6+7)^8)^9$	40870656	$(1+(2/3+4)^5)/6^{\wedge}(-7+8-9)$
36222433	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^{\wedge}((-6+78)/9)$	40994183	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3+4+5)^*(6+7^8))/9$
36350361	$-12+3*((4*5)^6-7^8*9)$	41437191	$-1-2+34*(5^6*78-9)$
36350364	$(1+2)*(-3+(4*5)^6-7^8*9)$	41437192	$-1*2+34*(5^6*78-9)$
36350382	$(1+2)*(3+(4*5)^6-7^8*9)$	41437193	$1-2+34*(5^6*78-9)$
36350385	$12+3*((4*5)^6-7^8*9)$	41437195	$1^2+34*(5^6*78-9)$
36909933	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6*(78-9)$	41437196	$1*2+34*(5^6*78-9)$
36984132	$(-1-2)*(3^4-5^6*789)$	41437197	$1+2+34*(5^6*78-9)$
36984339	$(1+2)*(-3*4+5^6*789)$	41437803	$-1-2+34*(5^6*78+9)$
36984354	$(1+2)*(-3-4+5^6*789)$	41437804	$-1*2+34*(5^6*78+9)$
36984360	$-1-2-3*(4-5^6*789)$	41437805	$1-2+34*(5^6*78+9)$
36984361	$1*-2-3*(4-5^6*789)$	41437807	$1^2+34*(5^6*78+9)$
36984362	$1-2-3*(4-5^6*789)$	41437808	$1*2+34*(5^6*78+9)$
36984363	$1^2*3*(-4+5^6*789)$	41437809	$1+2+34*(5^6*78+9)$
36984364	$1^2-3*(4-5^6*789)$	41530515	$(1+2/3)*((45+6^7)^8*89)$
36984365	$1*2-3*(4-5^6*789)$	41629545	$(1+2/3)*(4+5)^6*(7^8-9)$
36984366	$1+2-3*(4-5^6*789)$	41641937	$-1+234^{\wedge}(5+6-7)/8/9$
36984372	$(1+2)*(3-4+5^6*789)$	41641939	$1+234^{\wedge}(5+6-7)/8/9$
36984378	$(1+2)*(-3+4+5^6*789)$	42550093	$-1+2*((3^4-5)^6*7-89)$
36984384	$-1-2+3*(4+5^6*789)$	42550095	$1+2*((3^4-5)^6*7-89)$
36984385	$-1*2+3*(4+5^6*789)$	42550449	$-1+2*((3^4-5)^6*7+89)$
36984386	$1-2+3*(4+5^6*789)$	42550451	$1+2*((3^4-5)^6*7+89)$
36984387	$1^2*3*(4+5^6*789)$	42765534	$1-23*(4-5^6*7*(8+9))$
36984388	$1^2+3*(4+5^6*789)$	43011955	$(-1+2*3^4*(5^6-7))^*(8+9)$
36984389	$1*2+3*(4+5^6*789)$	43011989	$(1+2*3^4*(5^6-7))^*(8+9)$
36984390	$1+2+3*(4+5^6*789)$	43030995	$(-1+2*(3^4*5^6-7))^*(8+9)$
36984396	$(1+2)*(3+4+5^6*789)$	43031029	$(1+2*(3^4*5^6-7))^*(8+9)$
36984411	$(1+2)*(3*4+5^6*789)$	43031471	$(-1+2*(3^4*5^6+7))^*(8+9)$
36984618	$(1+2)*(3^4+5^6*789)$	43031505	$(1+2*(3^4*5^6+7))^*(8+9)$
37113058	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^6*(7-89)$	43050511	$(-1+2*3^4*(5^6+7))^*(8+9)$
37191183	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6*(78+9)$	43050545	$(1+2*3^4*(5^6+7))^*(8+9)$
37331808	$12^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^6*(7+89)$	43235899	$1/-2-(3*4-5/6/7^{\wedge}-8)^9$
37732926	$(-1+2*3^4)*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$	43235900	$1/2-(3*4-5/6/7^{\wedge}-8)^9$
37735824	$(-1+2*3^4)*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$	43235998	$1/-2+(3-4+5/6/7^{\wedge}-8)^9$
37744704	$(-1+2*3^4*5)^6*(7+8-9)$	43235999	$1/2+(3-4+5/6/7^{\wedge}-8)^9$
37838016	$(1+2*3^4*5)^6*(7+8-9)$	43236016	$1/-2-(3-4-5/6/7^{\wedge}-8)^9$
38201658	$(1+2*3^4)*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$	43236017	$1/2-(3-4-5/6/7^{\wedge}-8)^9$
38204592	$(1+2*3^4)*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$	43236115	$1/-2+(3*4+5/6/7^{\wedge}-8)^9$
38812356	$12*3*(-4+5^6*(78-9))$	43236116	$1/2+(3*4+5/6/7^{\wedge}-8)^9$
38812644	$12*3*(4+5^6*(78-9))$	43874675	$-1+(2+34)*(5^6*78-9)$
38924125	$-1/2+3/4*(5^6+7^8*9)$	43874677	$1+(2+34)*(5^6*78-9)$
38924126	$1/2+3/4*(5^6+7^8*9)$	43874748	$12*(3*(-4+5^6*78)-9)$
38937221	$-12-(3-4*5^6*7)^8*9$	43874820	$12*3*(4+5^6*78-9)$
38937245	$12-(3-4*5^6*7)^8*9$	43875180	$12*3*(-4+5^6*78+9)$
38937755	$-12+(3+4*5^6*7)^8*9$	43875252	$12*(3*(4+5^6*78)+9)$
39017875	$-1/2+3/4*(5^6+7^8)^9$	43875323	$-1+(2+34)*(5^6*78+9)$
39017876	$1/2+3/4*(5^6+7^8)^9$	43875325	$1+(2+34)*(5^6*78+9)$
39373551	$(1+(2+3)*(4-5^6*7)^8)^9$	44471358	$12*(3+4/5^6*7^8*9)$
39373569	$(1-(2+3)*(4-5^6*7)^8)^9$	44932797	$(-1+2^{\wedge}-3)*((4+5)^6-7^8*9)$
39374811	$(1+(2+3)*(4-5^6*7^8))^9$	45348643	$-1-2*(3^4*(5-6^7)+89)$
39374829	$(1-(2+3)*(4-5^6*7^8))^9$	45348645	$1-2*(3^4*(5-6^7)+89)$
39375171	$(-1+(2+3)*(4+5^6*7^8))^9$	45348999	$-1-2*(3^4*(5-6^7)-89)$
39375189	$(1+(2+3)*(4+5^6*7^8))^9$	45349001	$1-2*(3^4*(5-6^7)-89)$
39376431	$(-1+(2+3)*(4+5^6*7^8))^9$	45350263	$-1+2*(3^4*(5+6^7)-89)$
39376449	$(1+(2+3)*(4+5^6*7^8))^9$	45350265	$1+2*(3^4*(5+6^7)-89)$
39481361	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^4*567)^*(8+9)$	45350619	$-1+2*(3^4*(5+6^7)+89)$
40252455	$(-1-2*(3^4*5-6^7)*8)^9$	45350621	$1+2*(3^4*(5+6^7)+89)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
45397814	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3)^*(4-5-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	51884590	$1+23*(4+56)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$
45397821	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	51884642	$-1+(234+5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9$
46117832	$-12*(3+45-6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$	51884644	$1+(234+5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9$
46118984	$12*(3+45+6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$	51884853	$12*(3^{\wedge}4+56)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$
46120028	$12*(3^*45+6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$	51885488	$-1+(2+3)^*456+7^{\wedge}8^*9$
46124856	$-12*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$	51885490	$1+(2+3)^*456+7^{\wedge}8^*9$
46124999	$-1-(2+34)^*5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$	51885861	$-12*(3-4^*56)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$
46125001	$1-(2+34)^*5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$	51885933	$12*(3+4^*56)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$
46125144	$12*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$	51886413	$-12*(3-45^*6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$
46694835	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4/-5*(6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$	51899673	$(1+(2/(3+4))^{\wedge}5/6)/(7^{\wedge}8-9/9)$
46694844	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4/-5*(6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$	51924021	$-12+(3^{\wedge}4*56+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
47248263	$(1+2*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	51924045	$12+(3^{\wedge}4*56+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
47248281	$(1-2*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	52023599	$-1-234+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
47249775	$(1+2*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7^*8)^*9$	52023601	$1-234+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
47249793	$(1-2*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7^*8)^*9$	52024067	$-1+234+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
47250207	$(-1+2*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7^*8)^*9$	52024069	$1+234+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
47250225	$(1+2*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7^*8)^*9$	53488446	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3/4)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
47251719	$(-1+2*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	53999856	$12*3*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$
47251737	$(1+2*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	53999999	$-1+(2+34)^*5^{\wedge}6*(7+89)$
47471599	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$	54000001	$1+(2+34)^*5^{\wedge}6*(7+89)$
47471633	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$	54000144	$12*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$
47706607	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$	54607278	$(-1+234)^*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)-9)$
47706641	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$	54611472	$(-1+234)^*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)+9)$
48148813	$-1+2*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7-89)$	54841643	$-1+234*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)-9)$
48149169	$-1+2*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7+89)$	54841644	$1*234*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)-9)$
48149171	$1+2*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7+89)$	54841645	$1+234*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)-9)$
48515534	$1-23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)^*9)$	54843731	$1-(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7^*8^*9)$
48671856	$1-(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7^*8^*9)$	54845855	$-1+234*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)+9)$
48937356	$12*3*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	54845856	$1*234*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)+9)$
48937644	$12*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	54845857	$1+234*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)+9)$
49151399	$(-1+23^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7))/89$	55071616	$-1/2*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$
49774137	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))/9$	55076010	$(1+234)^*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)-9)$
49827797	$-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7*89)$	55080240	$(1+234)^*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)+9)$
49827799	$1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7*89)$	55124847	$(1+(2-(3+4)/5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
49829417	$-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7*89)$	55124865	$(1-(2-(3+4)/5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
49829419	$1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7*89)$	55124972	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7^*8^*9)$
50039928	$12*3*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	55125028	$(1+2*3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7^*8^*9)$
50040216	$12*3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	55125135	$(-1+(2+(3+4)/5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
50084784	$12*3*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	55125153	$(1+(2+(3+4)/5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
50085072	$12*3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	55555084	$(1+234)^*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9$
50246722	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3/4)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	56687076	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*5/6^{\wedge}7+8^*9)$
51011037	$(-1-2*3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$	57395524	$12*(3^{\wedge}4(4+5-6)-7^{\wedge}8/9)$
51011055	$(1-2*3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$	57395732	$12*(3^{\wedge}4(4+5-6)+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
51025617	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$	57646948	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4-5/(6/(7^{\wedge}8-9)))$
51025635	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$	57647128	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4-5/(6/(7^{\wedge}8+9)))$
51742349	$-1-234-(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	57647335	$(-12-3)^*(45-6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
51742351	$1-234-(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	57647767	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4-5*6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
51742817	$-1+234-(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	57647776	$-12*(3^*4-5/(6/(7^{\wedge}8-9)))$
51742819	$1+234-(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	57648244	$12*(3^*4+5/(6/(7^{\wedge}8+9)))$
51842373	$-12-(3^{\wedge}4*56-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	57648253	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4+5*6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
51842397	$12-(3^{\wedge}4*56-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	57648685	$(12+3)^*(45+6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
51880005	$12*(3-45^*6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	57648892	$12*(3^{\wedge}4+5/(6/(7^{\wedge}8-9)))$
51880485	$-12*(3+4^*56)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	57649072	$12*(3^{\wedge}4+5/(6/(7^{\wedge}8+9)))$
51880557	$12*(3-4^*56)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	57770739	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3)^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
51880928	$-1-(2+3)^*456+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	58368609	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3)^*((4-5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
51880930	$1-(2+3)^*456+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	58368618	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4-5-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
51881565	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+56)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	58368627	$(1+2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
51881774	$-1-(234+5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	58499532	$-12*(3-4*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9))$
51881776	$1-(234+5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	58499604	$12*(3+4*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9))$
51881828	$-1-23*(4+56)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	58500396	$-12*(3-4*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9))$
51881836	$1-(234-5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	58500468	$12*(3+4*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9))$
51882014	$1+23*(4-56)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	59463550	$1/(2-3^{\wedge}4)^*5*(6-7/8^{\wedge}9)$
51882530	$-1-2*(345-6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	60530410	$-1/2+(3^*4-5)/6*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
51882532	$1-2*(345-6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	60530411	$1/2+(3^*4-5)/6*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
51882601	$1/-2-(3^{\wedge}4*5/6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	60749976	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6)^*(7+8+9)$
51882602	$1/2-(3^{\wedge}4*5/6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	60750024	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6)^*(7+8+9)$
51883816	$-1/2+(3^{\wedge}4*5/6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	61328125	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4/5)^*(6+7-8)^{\wedge}9$
51883817	$1/2+(3^{\wedge}4*5/6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	61509387	$12+3*45^{\wedge}(6+7-8)/9$
51883886	$-1+2*(345-6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	61640604	$-1-(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$
51883888	$1+2*(345-6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	61640605	$(1+2+3)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$
51884404	$-1-23*(4-56)+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	61640606	$1-(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$
51884582	$-1+(234-5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	61640644	$-1+(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$

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61640645	$(1+2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	68025714	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)+8+9)$
61640646	$1+(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	68027580	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7+8)-9)$
61931511	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$	68027634	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$
61931529	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$	68139557	$(-12+(3+4)^*5^{\wedge}6*7)^*89$
62259851	$-1/(2+3)^*(4-5-6*7^{\wedge}8*9)$	68141693	$(12+(3+4)^*5^{\wedge}6*7)^*89$
62530944	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$	68205072	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8*9)$
62997687	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	68239392	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8-9)$
62997705	$(1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	68249376	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8-9)$
62999559	$(1+2*(3-4*5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*-9$	68250624	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8+9)$
62999577	$(1-2*(3-4*5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	68260608	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9)$
62999703	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$	68294928	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8*9)$
62999721	$(1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$	68423678	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8*9)$
62999955	$(1-2*(3-4*5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$	68458108	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8-9)$
63000045	$(-1+2*(3+4*5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$	68468124	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8-9)$
63000279	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$	68469376	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8+9)$
63000297	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$	68479392	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9)$
63000423	$(-1+2*(3+4*5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	68513822	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8*9)$
63000441	$(1+2*(3+4*5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	69123072	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*-56+7^{\wedge}8-9)$
63002295	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	69123288	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*-56+7^{\wedge}8+9)$
63002313	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	69231936	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*56+7^{\wedge}8-9)$
63823557	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-8)-9)$	69232152	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*56+7^{\wedge}8+9)$
63823611	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-8)+9)$	69609363	$-12+(3/45)^{\wedge}6*(7-8/9)$
63825192	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7-8*9)$	69609387	$12+(3/45)^{\wedge}6*(7-8/9)$
63825357	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7-8-9)$	69973065	$(1+2/3)*((4+5)^{\wedge}6*(7+8*9))$
63825405	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+8-9)$	72221397	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-8)-9)$
63825411	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7-8+9)$	72221451	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-8)+9)$
63825459	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+8+9)$	72223272	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7-8*9)$
63825624	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+8*9)$	72223437	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7-8-9)$
63827205	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8)-9)$	72223485	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7+8-9)$
63827259	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$	72223491	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7-8+9)$
65234375	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4/5)^*(6+7-8)^{\wedge}9$	72223539	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7+8+9)$
66410752	$1/2*((3^{\wedge}4-4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	72223704	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7+8*9)$
66452614	$1/2*(-3*4/5^{\wedge}6-7+8^{\wedge}9)$	72225525	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8)-9)$
66475768	$-1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)-8^{\wedge}9)$	72225579	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$
66476335	$-1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)-8^{\wedge}9)$	73088145	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*(3^{\wedge}4))^*(5^{\wedge}6/7*8-9)$
66720060	$-12*(3-4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	73124865	$(12+3)^*(4*5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
66720132	$12*(3+4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	73125135	$(12+3)^*(4*5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
66742488	$12*(-3+(4*5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	73161855	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*(3^{\wedge}4))^*(5^{\wedge}6/7*8+9)$
66757440	$12*(-3+(4*5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	73968725	$-1-2*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$
66757512	$12*(3+(4*5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	73968726	$(1+2+3)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$
66779868	$-12*(3-4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	73968727	$1-2*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$
66779940	$12*(3+4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	73968773	$-1+2*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$
67053893	$1/2*((3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)^*-7+8^{\wedge}9)$	73968774	$(1+2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$
67054136	$-1/2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	73968775	$1+2*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$
67054217	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	76781238	$-12+(3+4)^*5^{\wedge}6*78*9$
67054460	$1/2*((3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)^*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	76781262	$12+(3+4)^*5^{\wedge}6*78*9$
67100359	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6*-7+8^{\wedge}9)$	77759928	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*-9$
67107268	$1/2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*-6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	77759946	$(1-(2-3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
67108305	$-1/2*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6+7)-8^{\wedge}9)$	77771304	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*-9$
67108415	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*(-5-6)-7+8^{\wedge}9)$	77771322	$(1-(2-3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
67108422	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*(-5-6)+7+8^{\wedge}9)$	77874967	$-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
67108542	$1/2*((3^{\wedge}4+5+6)^*-7+8^{\wedge}9)$	77874969	$1-2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
67163268	$1/2*((3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)^*-7+8^{\wedge}9)$	77875031	$-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
67163511	$1/2*(-3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	77875033	$1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
67163592	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	77959440	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$
67163835	$1/2*((3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)^*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	77970672	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$
67741393	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)+8^{\wedge}9)$	78029328	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$
67741960	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)+8^{\wedge}9)$	78040560	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$
67931136	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}4*5)^*6^{\wedge}(-7+8+9)$	78209310	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$
68021262	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$	78220578	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$
68021316	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7+8)-9)$	78279422	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$
68023182	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)+8+9)$	78290690	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$
68023230	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)-8+9)$	79554263	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}4/5)^*(6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
68023236	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)+8-9)$	80985159	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4/5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
68023284	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)-8-9)$	80985177	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4/5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
68023692	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7-8)-9)$	81655647	$(-1+2*34)^*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
68023746	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7-8)+9)$	81656853	$(-1+2*34)^*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
68025150	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7-8)+9)$	81697140	$(-1+(2+3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
68025204	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7-8)-9)$	81697158	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
68025612	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)-8-9)$	81709092	$(-1+(2+3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
68025660	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)+8-9)$	81709110	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
68025666	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)-8+9)$	82874387	$-1+2*34*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
82874389	$1+2*34*(5^6*78-9)$	98825160	$(-1-2/3)/((4-5-6)^{-7/8}/9)$
82875611	$-1+2*34*(5^6*78+9)$	100086528	$(1+2)/(3^4-5)^{(6+7-8-9)}$
82875613	$1+2*34*(5^6*78+9)$	100527975	$(1+(2+(3^4-4-5)^6)^7)^8)^{-9}$
83236920	$(-1-2)*((3-4*5)^6-7^8*9)$	100527993	$(1-(2+(3^4-4-5)^6)^7)^8)^9$
84093129	$(1+2*34)*(5^6*78-9)$	100528263	$(-1+(2-(3^4-4-5)^6)^7)^8)^9$
84094371	$(1+2*34)*(5^6*78+9)$	100528281	$(1+(2-(3^4-4-5)^6)^7)^8)^9$
84817537	$(-1+2^3)*(4*5)^6-7^8*9)$	100563646	$(1+(2*3^4-5)^*(6-7^8))/-9$
86092425	$(1-2*(3^4(4*5-6)-7*8))^*-9$	101025639	$(1+(2-(3^4-4+5)^6)^7)^8)^*-9$
86092443	$(1+2*(3^4(4*5-6)-7*8))^*9$	101025657	$(1-(2-(3^4-4+5)^6)^7)^8)^*9$
86093163	$(-1+2*(3^4(4*5-6)-7-8))^*9$	101025927	$(-1+(2+(3^4-4+5)^6)^7)^8)^*9$
86093181	$(1+2*(3^4(4*5-6)-7-8))^*9$	101025945	$(1+(2+(3^4-4+5)^6)^7)^8)^*9$
86093415	$(-1+2*(3^4(4*5-6)+7-8))^*9$	101249973	$(1+2)*(3^4-4*(5*6)^{7/8-9})$
86093469	$(1+2*(3^4(4*5-6)+7+8))^*9$	101250027	$(1+2)*(3^4-4*(5*6)^{7/8+9})$
86093703	$(-1+2*(3^4(4*5-6)+7+8))^*9$	103485099	$-1-2*(34+(5^6*7^8)^9)$
86093721	$(1+2*(3^4(4*5-6)+7+8))^*9$	103485237	$1+2*(34-(5^6*7^8)^9)$
86094441	$(1-2*(3^4(4*5-6)+7*8))^*-9$	103735099	$-1-2*(34+5^6*7^8)^9)$
86094459	$(1+2*(3^4(4*5-6)+7*8))^*9$	103735101	$1-2*(34+5^6*7^8)^9)$
86296847	$(1+2*3*(4+5^6*789))$	103735235	$-1+2*(34-5^6*7^8)^9)$
86296903	$(1+2*3*(4+5^6*789))$	103735237	$1+2*(34-5^6*7^8)^9)$
86470548	$(1+2*(3^4-5/6/7^8-8))^*-9$	103750371	$(1+2*(3^4*(5+6)-7^8))^*-9$
86470566	$(1-2*(3^4-5/6/7^8-8))^*9$	103750389	$(1-2*(3^4*(5+6)-7^8))^*9$
86471193	$-12-3*45*(6-7^8/9)$	103757121	$(1+2*((3^4+5)^6*7^8))^*-9$
86471217	$12-3*45*(6-7^8/9)$	103757139	$(1-2*((3^4+5)^6*7^8))^*9$
86472813	$-12+3*45*(6+7^8/9)$	103757345	$-1-2*(3^4*5^6-7^8)^9)$
86472837	$12+3*45*(6+7^8/9)$	103757347	$1-2*(3^4*5^6-7^8)^9)$
86473464	$(-1+2*(3^4+5/6/7^8-8))^*9$	103758201	$(1+2*((3^4-5)^6*7^8))^*-9$
86473482	$(1+2*(3^4+5/6/7^8-8))^*9$	103758219	$(1-2*((3^4-5)^6*7^8))^*9$
87749967	$-1-2^3*(4-5^6*78^9)$	103759011	$(1+2*(3^4*5+6-7^8))^*-9$
87749969	$1-2^3*(4-5^6*78^9)$	103759029	$(1-2*(3^4*5+6-7^8))^*9$
87750031	$-1+2^3*(4+5^6*78^9)$	103759227	$(1+2*(3^4*5+6-7^8))^*-9$
87750033	$1+2^3*(4+5^6*78^9)$	103759245	$(1-2*(3^4*5+6-7^8))^*9$
87890454	$(-1-(2+3)*(4-5^6(-6+7+8)))^*9$	103762277	$-1-2*(345*6-7^8)^9)$
87890796	$(-1+(2+3)*(4+5^6(-6+7+8)))^*9$	103762279	$1-2*(345*6-7^8)^9)$
88835175	$(1+(2-3^4)*(5^6-7)^8)^*-9$	103765176	$(-1-2)*(3^4*5-6*7^8+9)$
88835193	$(1-(2-3^4)*(5^6-7)^8)^*9$	103765365	$(-1-2)*(3^4*5-6*(7^8+9))$
88914807	$(1+(2-3^4)*(5^6+7)^8)^*-9$	103765669	$-1-2*(34*(5+6)-7^8)^9)$
88914825	$(1-(2-3^4)*(5^6+7)^8)^*9$	103765841	$-1-2*((3+45)^6*7^8)^9)$
88942548	$12/(3+4)*(-56+7^8/9)$	103765883	$-1+2*(3-45*6+7^8)^9)$
88942740	$12/(3+4)*(56+7^8/9)$	103765949	$-1-2*((34+5)^6*7^8)^9)$
91084023	$(1+(2-3^4*(5^6-7))^8)^*-9$	103766089	$-1-2*(34*5-6-7^8)^9)$
91084041	$(1-(2-3^4*(5^6-7))^8)^*9$	103766145	$1-2*(3^4+5^6-7^8)^9)$
91084311	$(-1+(2+3^4*(5^6-7))^8)^*9$	103766691	$-1+2*(3^4+5^6+7^8)^9)$
91084329	$(1+(2+3^4*(5^6-7))^8)^*9$	103766887	$1+2*((34+5)^6*7^8)^9)$
91165671	$(1+(2-3^4*(5^6+7))^8)^*-9$	103766995	$1+2*((3+45)^6*7^8)^9)$
91165689	$(1-(2-3^4*(5^6+7))^8)^*9$	103767167	$1+2*(34*(5+6)+7^8)^9)$
91165959	$(-1+(2+3^4*(5^6+7))^8)^*9$	103767471	$(1+2)*(3^4*5+6*(7^8-9))$
91165977	$(1+(2+3^4*(5^6+7))^8)^*9$	103767660	$(1+2)*(3^4*5+6*7^8+9)$
92228752	$12*3*4*(-56+7^8/9)$	103770557	$-1+2*(345*6+7^8)^9)$
92235736	$(-1-23)*(45-6*7^8/9)$	103770559	$1+2*(345*6+7^8)^9)$
92237896	$(1+23)*(45+6*7^8/9)$	103773591	$(1-2*(3^4*5-6+7^8))^*-9$
92244880	$12*3*4*(56+7^8/9)$	103773609	$(1+2*(3^4*5-6+7^8))^*9$
93333159	$(-1+(2+3^4*(5^6-7)^8)^*9$	103773807	$(1-2*(3^4*5+6+7^8))^*-9$
93333177	$(1+(2+3^4*(5^6-7)^8)^*9$	103773825	$(1+2*(3^4*5+6+7^8))^*9$
93416823	$(-1+(2+3^4*(5^6+7)^8)^*9$	103774617	$(-1+2*((3^4-5)^6*7^8))^*9$
93416841	$(1+(2+3^4*(5^6+7)^8)^*9$	103774635	$(1+2*((3^4-5)^6*7^8))^*9$
94499847	$(1+(2-3^4/(5^6-6/7))^8)^*-9$	103775489	$-1+2*(3^4*5^6+7^8)^9)$
94499865	$(1-(2-3^4/(5^6-6/7))^8)^*9$	103775491	$1+2*(3^4*5^6+7^8)^9)$
94500135	$(-1+(2+3^4/(5^6-6/7))^8)^*9$	103775697	$(-1+2*((3^4+5)^6*7^8))^*9$
94500153	$(1+(2+3^4/(5^6-6/7))^8)^*9$	103775715	$(1+2*((3^4+5)^6*7^8))^*9$
95119216	$-1/2-(3-4-5/6)*7^8/9$	103782447	$(-1+2*(3^4*(5+6)+7^8))^*9$
95119217	$1/2-(3-4-5/6)*7^8/9$	103782465	$(1+2*(3^4*(5+6)+7^8))^*9$
97361185	$(1+2*(3^4-5)^*(6+7^8))/9$	103797599	$-1-2*(34-5^6*7^8)^9)$
98624967	$-1-2^3*(4-5^6*789)$	103797601	$1-2*(34-5^6*7^8)^9)$
98624968	$1*2^3*(4+5^6*789)$	103797735	$-1+2*(34+5^6*7^8)^9)$
98624969	$1-2^3*(4-5^6*789)$	103797737	$1+2*(34+5^6*7^8)^9)$
98625031	$-1+2^3*(4+5^6*789)$	104047599	$-1-2*(34-(5^6+7^8)^9)$
98625032	$1*2^3*(4+5^6*789)$	104047600	$1+2*(34-(5^6+7^8)^9)$
98625033	$1+2^3*(4+5^6*789)$	104047736	$1*2*(34+(5^6+7^8)^9)$
98718009	$-12+3^4*(5^6*78-9)$	104047737	$1+2*(34+(5^6+7^8)^9)$
98718033	$12+3^4*(5^6*78-9)$	105402465	$(1+2/3)/((4+5)^{-6/7}/(8+9))$
98719467	$-12+3^4*(5^6*78+9)$	106225992	$12*3^4*(5^6*7-89)$
98719491	$12+3^4*(5^6*78+9)$	106399008	$12*3^4*(5^6*7+89)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
106968974	$(1 - (2^*3^4+5)^*(6-7^8))/9$	129708021	$1/2^*(-3+(4-5+6)^*7^8*9)$
109979871	$(-12+3^4*5)^*(6^7-89)$	129708048	$1/2^*(3^4-5^*(6-7^8*9))$
110049825	$(-12+3^4*5)^*(6^7+89)$	129708078	$1/2^*(3^4+5^*(6+7^8*9))$
110905431	$(-1+23^4)^*(5^6*78-9)$	129708130	$1/-2+3^*(4+5/6/7^8-8)^*9$
110907069	$(-1+23^4)^*(5^6*78+9)$	129708131	$1/2+3^*(4+5/6/7^8)^*9$
112124171	$-1+23^4*(5^6*78-9)$	130421230	$(1+2^*(3^4(4^*5)/6+7^8))/9$
112124173	$1+23^4*(5^6*78-9)$	130691211	$-12-(3-45)^(6+7-8)-9$
112125827	$-1+23^4*(5^6*78+9)$	131616252	$12^*(-3^4+5^6*78)^*9$
112125829	$1+23^4*(5^6*78+9)$	131624244	$12^*(-3-4+5^6*78)^*9$
112589094	$(-12+3^4*(5^6-7))^*89$	131624532	$-12^*(3+(4-5^6*78)^*9)$
112590150	$-12+3^4*(5^6-7)^*89$	131624604	$12^*(3-(4-5^6*78)^*9)$
112590174	$12+3^4*(5^6-7)^*89$	131624916	$12^*(-3-4+5^6*78)^*9$
112591230	$(12+3^4*(5^6-7))^*89$	131625084	$12^*(3+4+5^6*78)^*9$
112690020	$(-12+3^4*(5^6+7))^*89$	131625396	$12^*(-3+(4+5^6*78)^*9)$
112691076	$-12+3^4*(5^6+7)^*89$	131625468	$12^*(3+(4+5^6*78)^*9)$
112691100	$12+3^4*(5^6+7)^*89$	131625756	$12^*(3+4+5^6*78)^*9$
112692156	$(12+3^4*(5^6+7))^*89$	131633748	$12^*(3^4+5^6*78)^*9$
112873839	$(1+2^*(3+4))^*(5^6*7^8-9)$	132591664	$-1+23^*(4+5)^*(6+7^8/9)$
112876161	$(1+2^*(3+4))^*(5^6*7^8+9)$	132677632	$(1-(2^3)^4-4^*(5+6^*7))^*8^9$
113338023	$-12+3^4*5^*(6^7-89)$	133005312	$(1+(2^4-3)^4)^*(5-6^*7))^*8^9$
113338047	$12+3^4*5^*(6^7-89)$	134163212	$-12^*(3^4*5^6+7)+8^9$
113342913	$(1+23^4)^*(5^6*78-9)$	134163380	$-12^*(3^4*5^6-7)+8^9$
113344587	$(1+23^4)^*(5^6*78+9)$	134211884	$-12-3^4*(5+6^7)+8^9$
113366859	$-12+3^4*(5^6*78-89)$	134212064	$-12^*(3^4*5+6^7)+8^9$
113366883	$12+3^4*(5^6*78-89)$	134212694	$-12+3^4*(5-6^7)+8^9$
113381277	$-12+3^4*(5^6*78+89)$	134212718	$12+3^4*(5-6^7)+8^9$
113381301	$12+3^4*(5^6*78+89)$	134213672	$-12^*(3^4*5-6^7)+8^9$
113410113	$-12+3^4*5^*(6^7+89)$	134221784	$12^*(3^4*5-6^7)+8^9$
113410137	$12+3^4*5^*(6^7+89)$	134222738	$-12-3^4*(5-6^7)+8^9$
114791061	$(1+2)^*((3^4(4^*5-6)-7)^*8-9)$	134222762	$12-3^4*(5-6^7)+8^9$
114791115	$(1+2)^*((3^4(4^*5-6)-7)^*8+9)$	134223392	$12^*(3^4*5+6^7)+8^9$
114791397	$(1+2)^*((3^4(4^*5-6)+7)^*8-9)$	134223572	$12+3^4*(5+6^7)+8^9$
114791451	$(1+2)^*((3^4(4^*5-6)+7)^*8+9)$	134272076	$12^*(3^4*5^6-7)+8^9$
115638272	$(1-(2^4-3)^4*5^6)^*8^9$	134272244	$12^*(3^4*5^6+7)+8^9$
116696199	$(12+3^4*5^*(6^7-89))$	135757824	$(1+(2^4-3)^4)^*(5+6^*7))^*8^9$
116770425	$(12+3^4*5^*(6^7+89))$	136048479	$-12-3^4*(5-6^7(7-8+9))$
116808192	$-12^*(3+(4-5^6*7)^*89)$	136048503	$12-3^4*(5-6^7(7-8+9))$
116808264	$12^*(3-(4-5^6*7)^*89)$	136049289	$-12+3^4*(5+6^7(7-8+9))$
116812416	$12^*(-3-4+5^6*7^*89)$	136049313	$12+3^4*(5+6^7(7-8+9))$
116812584	$12^*(3+4+5^6*7^*89)$	136687381	$12/(3/45)^6-7^*(8+9)$
116813568	$(12+3^4/5^6-6^*7)^*89$	136687499	$12/(3/45)^6+(7-8)^9$
116816736	$12^*(-3+(4+5^6*7)^*89)$	136687501	$12/(3/45)^6-(7-8)^9$
116816808	$12^*(3+(4+5^6*7)^*89)$	136687565	$12/(3/45)^6+7^*8+9$
117647639	$(-1+2/3^4*5)^*(6-7-8^9)$	136687579	$12/(3/45)^6+7^*8+9$
117900891	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4^*(5+6)+7^8*9)$	136687619	$12/(3/45)^6+7^*(8+9)$
121059606	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5-5+(6-7+8)^9)$	138353604	$12^*3^*(-45+6^*7^8/9)$
121062036	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5+(6-7+8)^9)$	140873551	$(-1+2/3^4-4)^*(5^6*7^*8-9)$
123795904	$1/2^*(3^4*5^6*7^8+8^9)$	140876449	$(-1+2/3^4-4)^*(5^6*7^*8+9)$
124061949	$(-1+(2-3/4)^5)^*6^7(-7+8+9)$	141547385	$(1-(2^*3)^4)^*(5^6*7^*8+9)$
124262868	$(12+(3^4-4-5)^*6^7)^*-89$	141618610	$(-1+(2^*3)^4)^*(5^6*7-8-9)$
124263924	$-12-(3^4-4-5)^*6^7*89$	141639330	$(-1+(2^*3)^4)^*(5^6*7+8-9)$
124263948	$12-(3^4-4-5)^*6^7*89$	141641920	$(-1+(2^*3)^4)^*(5^6*7-8+9)$
124265004	$(12-(3^4-4-5)^*6^7)^*89$	141662640	$(-1+(2^*3)^4)^*(5^6*7+8+9)$
124564299	$-12-(3^4-5^6*7)^*89$	141733865	$(1-(2^*3)^4)^*(5^6*7-8^*9)$
124564323	$12-(3^4-5^6*7)^*89$	141765991	$(1+(2^*3)^4)^*(5^6*7-8^*9)$
124578717	$-12+(3^4+5^6*7)^*89$	141837326	$(1+(2^*3)^4)^*(5^6*7-8-9)$
124578741	$12+(3^4+5^6*7)^*89$	141858078	$(1+(2^*3)^4)^*(5^6*7+8-9)$
124878036	$(-12+(3^4-4+5)^*6^7)^*89$	141860672	$(1+(2^*3)^4)^*(5^6*7-8+9)$
124879092	$-12+(3^4-4+5)^*6^7*89$	141881424	$(1+(2^*3)^4)^*(5^6*7+8+9)$
124879116	$12+(3^4-4+5)^*6^7*89$	141952759	$(1+(2^*3)^4)^*(5^6*7+8^*9)$
124880172	$(12+(3^4-4+5)^*6^7)^*89$	142452310	$12/(3/45)^6+7^8+9$
125990775	$(-1+2^*(3+4))^*(5^6*7-8)^*9$	142623533	$(1+2/3^4-4)^*(5^6*7^*8-9)$
125990793	$(1+2^*(3+4))^*(5^6*7-8)^*9$	142626467	$(1+2/3^4-4)^*(5^6*7^*8+9)$
126009207	$(-1+2^*(3+4))^*(5^6*7+8)^*9$	143066703	$-12-3^*(4^*(5+6)-7^8*9)$
126009225	$(1+2^*(3+4))^*(5^6*7+8)^*9$	143066706	$(1+2)^*(-3-4^*(5+6)+7^8*9)$
126547659	$(-1+2^*(3^4*5^6+7^8))^*9$	143066724	$(1+2)^*(3-4^*(5+6)+7^8*9)$
126547677	$(1+2^*(3^4*5^6+7^8))^*9$	143066727	$12-3^*(4^*(5+6)-7^8*9)$
127398343	$(-1+2^*(3+4+5)^*(6^7-8))/9$	143935479	$(-1+2^*(3+4)^*(5^6-7)^*8)^*9$
127405625	$(1+2^*(3+4+5)^*(6^7+8))/9$	143935497	$(1+2^*(3+4)^*(5^6-7)^*8)^*9$
127859096	$(-1+2^*(3^4(4^*5)/6-7^8))/9$	144064503	$(-1+2^*(3+4)^*(5^6+7)^*8)^*9$
129707914	$1/-2-3^*(4-5/6/7^8-8)^*9$	144064521	$(1+2^*(3+4)^*(5^6+7)^*8)^*9$
129707915	$1/2-3^*(4-5/6/7^8-8)^*9$	144119788	$-12+(3^4-56)^*(7^8-9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
144119812	$12+(3^4-56)*(7^8-9)$	155602776	$12+3*(4-5^6+7^8*9)$
144120238	$-12+(3^4-56)*(7^8+9)$	155602788	$(1+2)*(3^4-5^6+7^8*9)$
144120262	$12+(3^4-56)*(7^8+9)$	155602995	$(1+2)*(3^4-5^6+7^8*9)$
145272825	$(1+(2+3^4)/(5/(6-7^8)))^*-9$	155631141	$(1+2)*((-3-4^5)^*6+7^8*9)$
145272843	$(1-2*(3+4)/(5/(6-7^8)))^*9$	155631183	$-12-3*(4^5*6-7^8*9)$
146015565	$(12+3)*(-4+5^6*7^8*9)$	155631186	$(1+2)*(-3-4^5*6+7^8*9)$
146015685	$(12+3)*(4+5^6*7^8*9)$	155631195	$(1-2)*3*(4^5*6-7^8*9)$
146228575	$-1-234*(5^6-7^8/9)$	155631204	$(1+2)*(3-4^5*6+7^8*9)$
146228576	$-1*234*(5^6-7^8/9)$	155631207	$12-3*(4^5*6-7^8*9)$
146228577	$1-234*(5^6-7^8/9)$	155631249	$(1+2)*((3-4^5)^*6+7^8*9)$
146244384	$(-1+(2+3)^4)*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$	155637339	$(-1-2)*((3-4+5)^6-7^8*9)$
146255616	$(-1+(2+3)^4)*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$	155640357	$(1+2)*(-3*(4^5+6)+7^8*9)$
146691675	$(-1-2)*((3+4+5)^6-7^8*9)$	155640393	$(1+2)*(-3*4^5-6+7^8*9)$
146713116	$(1+(2+3)^4)*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$	155640429	$(1+2)*(-3*4^5+6+7^8*9)$
146724384	$(1+(2+3)^4)*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$	155640465	$(1+2)*(-3*(4^5-6)+7^8*9)$
146890608	$(1+(2-3^4)^5*5^6*7^8)*(-8-9)$	155643417	$(1+2)*(-345*6+7^8*9)$
146890642	$(1-(2-3^4)^5*5^6*7^8)*(8+9)$	155645523	$(1+2)*(-3*456+7^8*9)$
147002425	$-1/2-(3-4^5)/(6*7^8-8/9)$	155646525	$-12-3*(4^5+6-7^8*9)$
147002426	$1/2-(3-4^5)/(6*7^8-8/9)$	155646549	$12-3*(4^5+6-7^8*9)$
149877805	$-1-234*(5^6-7^8/9)$	155646561	$-12-3*(4^5-6-7^8*9)$
149877806	$1*234*(-5^6+7^8/9)$	155646585	$12-3*(4^5-6-7^8*9)$
149877807	$1-234*(5^6-7^8/9)$	155648256	$-1-2-3*(456-7^8*9)$
149882251	$-1-234*(5+6-7^8/9)$	155648257	$1*-2-3*(456-7^8*9)$
149882252	$1*234*(-5-6+7^8/9)$	155648258	$1-2-3*(456-7^8*9)$
149882253	$1-234*(5+6-7^8/9)$	155648260	$1^2-3*(456-7^8*9)$
149884630	$-1-234*(5/6-7^8/9)$	155648261	$1^2-3*(456-7^8*9)$
149884631	$-1*234*(5/6-7^8/9)$	155648394	$(1+2)*(3^4*-5-6+7^8*9)$
149884632	$1-234*(5/6-7^8/9)$	155648610	$(1+2)*(-345+6+7^8*9)$
149887399	$-1+234*(5+6+7^8/9)$	155648967	$12-3*(4^5*6-7^8*9)$
149887400	$1*234*(5+6+7^8/9)$	155648997	$(1+2)*((3+4)^5*5^6-6+7^8*9)$
149887401	$1+234*(5+6+7^8/9)$	155649103	$-12-3*(4^5/6-7^8*9)$
149891845	$-1+234*(5^6+7^8/9)$	155649106	$(-1-2)*(3+4^5/6-7^8*9)$
149891846	$1*234*(5^6+7^8/9)$	155649124	$(1+2)*(3-4^5/6+7^8*9)$
149891847	$1+234*(5^6+7^8/9)$	155649127	$12-3*(4^5/6-7^8*9)$
150787819	$(-1-2/3^4*5^6)*(6-7-8^9)$	155649809	$1*2+3*(4+5+6+7^8*9)$
150866658	$(1+2)*(-3*(4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	155650127	$-12+3*(4^5/6+7^8*9)$
151061055	$(1+2/3)*(-4^5+(6+7)^8)/9$	155650130	$(-1-2)*(3-4^5/6-7^8*9)$
151170651	$(-1-2)*((3^4)^4*5^6-7^8*9)$	155650148	$(1+2)*(3+4^5/6+7^8*9)$
152797184	$(1+(2^4-3)^4*5^6*7^8)^*8^9$	155650151	$12+3*(4^5/6+7^8*9)$
153541075	$-1+234*(5^6+7^8/9)$	155650257	$(1+2)*((3+4)^5*5^6+7^8*9)$
153541076	$1*234*(5^6+7^8/9)$	155650287	$-12+3*(4^5+6+7^8*9)$
153541077	$1+234*(5^6+7^8/9)$	155650644	$(1+2)*(345-6+7^8*9)$
154055292	$-12-3*((4+5)^6-7^8*9)$	155650860	$(1+2)*(3^4*5+6+7^8*9)$
154055295	$(-1-2)*(3+(4+5)^6-7^8*9)$	155650993	$-1*2+3*(456+7^8*9)$
154055313	$(1+2)*(3-(4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	155650994	$1-2+3*(456+7^8*9)$
154055316	$12-3*((4+5)^6-7^8*9)$	155650996	$1^2+3*(456+7^8*9)$
154328108	$(-1+(2+3^4)^5*5^6*7^8)*(8+9)$	155650997	$1*2+3*(456+7^8*9)$
154328142	$(1+(2+3^4)^5*5^6*7^8)*(8+9)$	155650998	$1+2+3*(456+7^8*9)$
154903113	$(1+2)*((-3^4)^5-6+7^8*9)$	155652669	$-12+3*(4^5-6+7^8*9)$
154903149	$(1+2)*((-3^4)^5+6+7^8*9)$	155652693	$12+3*(4^5-6+7^8*9)$
155087127	$(1+2)*(-3^4/5^6-6+7^8*9)$	155652705	$-12+3*(4^5+6+7^8*9)$
155227728	$-12-3*(4+(5^6-7^8)^*9)$	155652729	$12+3*(4^5+6+7^8*9)$
155227776	$12+3*(4-(5^6-7^8)^*9)$	155653731	$(1+2)*(3^4*5+6+7^8*9)$
155295333	$(1+2)*(-3^4(4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	155655837	$(1+2)*(345*6+7^8*9)$
155296680	$(-1-2)*((3^4-5)^6-7^8*9)$	155658789	$(1+2)*(3*(4^5-6)+7^8*9)$
155321502	$(1+2)*((-3-4)^5*5^6+7^8*9)$	155658825	$(1+2)*(3^4*5-6+7^8*9)$
155347101	$(1+2)*((-3-4)^5*6+7^8*9)$	155658861	$(1+2)*(3^4*5+6+7^8*9)$
155462115	$-12-3*(4^5*5^6-7^8*9)$	155658897	$(1+2)*(3*(4^5+6)+7^8*9)$
155462118	$(1+2)*(-3-4^5*5^6+7^8*9)$	155661915	$(1+2)*((3-4+5)^6+7^8*9)$
155462136	$(1+2)*(3-4^5*5^6+7^8*9)$	155668005	$(1+2)*((-3+4^5)^6+7^8*9)$
155462139	$12-3*(4^5*5^6-7^8*9)$	155668047	$-12+3*(4^5*6+7^8*9)$
155508966	$(1+2)*(-3^4(4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	155668050	$(1+2)*(-3+4^5*6+7^8*9)$
155509038	$(1+2)*(3*(4-5^6)+7^8*9)$	155668059	$(-1+2)*3*(4^5*6+7^8*9)$
155509659	$(-1-2)*((3-4-5)^6-7^8*9)$	155668068	$(1+2)*(3+4^5*6+7^8*9)$
155590560	$(-1-2)*(3^4(4+5)^6-7^8*9)$	155668071	$12+3*(4^5*6+7^8*9)$
155590596	$(-1-2)*(3^4(4+5)^6-7^8*9)$	155668113	$(1+2)*((3+4^5)^6+7^8*9)$
155594331	$(1+2)*(3/4^5-5^6-6+7^8*9)$	155696259	$(1+2)*(-3^4+5^6+7^8*9)$
155599188	$(-1-2)*((3+4)^5+6-7^8*9)$	155696466	$(1+2)*(-3^4+5^6+7^8*9)$
155599224	$(-1-2)*((3+4)^5-6-7^8*9)$	155696478	$-12-3*(4-5^6-7^8*9)$
155602509	$(-1-2)*(3^4+5^6-7^8*9)$	155696526	$12+3*(4+5^6+7^8*9)$
155602716	$(1+2)*(3^4-5^6+7^8*9)$	155696538	$(1+2)*(3^4+5^6+7^8*9)$
155602728	$-12-3*(4+5^6-7^8*9)$	155696745	$(1+2)*(3^4+5^6+7^8*9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
155700030	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^5-6+7^8*9)$	188839296	$12^3*(-4+5^6*7-89)$
155700066	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^5+6+7^8*9)$	188853120	$12^3*(4+5^6*7-89)$
155704923	$(1+2)^*(3/4^5-5*6+7^8*9)$	188999991	$(-1+2^3*4*5^6*7*8)^*9$
155708658	$(1+2)^*(3^4(4+5)-6+7^8*9)$	189000009	$(1+2^3*4/(5^6-6/7/8))^*9$
155708694	$(1+2)^*(3^4(4+5)+6+7^8*9)$	189146880	$12^3*(-4+5^6*7+89)$
155789595	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4-5)^6+7^8*9)$	189160704	$12^3*(4+5^6*7+89)$
155790216	$(1+2)^*(3^4(-4+5^6)+7^8*9)$	193398363	$(1+2)^*(3/4^4(-5-6)+7^8*9)$
155790288	$(1+2)^*(3^4(4+5^6)+7^8*9)$	194637253	$-1+2^*(34^5-6+7^8*9)$
155837115	$-12+3^*(4^5+6+7^8*9)$	194637255	$1+2^*(34^5-6+7^8*9)$
155837118	$(1+2)^*(-3+4^5+6+7^8*9)$	194637277	$-1+2^*(34^5+6+7^8*9)$
155837136	$(1+2)^*(3+4^5+6+7^8*9)$	194637279	$1+2^*(34^5+6+7^8*9)$
155837139	$12+3^*(4^5+6+7^8*9)$	198885634	$-1/2+(3+4^5)/(6/(7^8*9))$
155952153	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^5+6+7^8*9)$	198885635	$1/2+(3+4^5)/(6/(7^8*9))$
155977752	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^5+6+7^8*9)$	201542247	$(-1-2^*(3^4-5/6^7-7)^*8)^*9$
156002574	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5)^6+7^8*9)$	201542265	$(1-2^*(3^4-5/6^7-7)^*8)^*9$
156003921	$(1+2)^*(3^4(4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	201565575	$(-1+2^*(3^4+5/6^7-7)^*8)^*9$
156071466	$(1+2)^*(-3^4+(5^6+7^8)^*9)$	201565593	$(1+2^*(3^4+5/6^7-7)^*8)^*9$
156071478	$-12-3^*(4-(5^6+7^8)^*9)$	203872903	$(-1+234)^*(5^6+7^8-9)$
156071526	$12+3^*(4+(5^6+7^8)^*9)$	203877097	$(-1+234)^*(5^6*7^8+9)$
156071538	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6+7^8)^*9)$	204067095	$-12-3^4*(5-(6^7-8)^*9)$
156212127	$(1+2)^*(3^4/5^6-6+7^8*9)$	204067119	$-12-3^4*(5-(6^7-8)^*9)$
156396105	$(1+2)^*((3^4)^5-6+7^8*9)$	204067905	$-12+3^4*(5+(6^7-8)^*9)$
156396141	$(1+2)^*((3^4)^5+6+7^8*9)$	204067929	$12+3^4*(5+(6^7-8)^*9)$
157243938	$-12+3^*((4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	204078759	$-12-3^4*(5-(6^7+8)^*9)$
157243941	$(1+2)^*(-3+(4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	204078783	$12-3^4*(5-(6^7+8)^*9)$
157243959	$(1+2)^*(3+(4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	204079569	$-12+3^4*(5+(6^7+8)^*9)$
157243962	$12+3^*((4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	204079593	$12+3^4*(5+(6^7+8)^*9)$
159457077	$(-1+2/3^4-4^*(5^6*7-8))^*9$	204747893	$-1+234^*(5^6*7^8-9)$
159457095	$(1+2/3^4-4^*(5^6*7-8))^*9$	204747895	$1+234^*(5^6*7^8-9)$
159468660	$-1+2/((3/45)^6/7)-89$	204752105	$-1+234^*(5^6*7^8+9)$
159468662	$1+2/((3/45)^6/7)-89$	204752107	$1+234^*(5^6*7^8+9)$
159468838	$-1+2/((3/45)^6/7)+89$	205622885	$(1+234)^*(5^6*7^8-9)$
159468840	$1+2/((3/45)^6/7)+89$	205627115	$(1+234)^*(5^6*7^8+9)$
159480405	$(-1+2/3^4-4^*(5^6*7+8))^*9$	207530884	$-12^3-4^*(56-7^8*9)$
159480423	$(1+2/3^4-4^*(5^6*7+8))^*9$	207531332	$-12^3+4^*(56+7^8*9)$
160128603	$(1+2)^*((3^4)^5+6+7^8*9)$	207532588	$-1-23-4^*(56-7^8*9)$
160432596	$(1+2)^*(3^4(4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	207532589	$1^*-23-4^*(56-7^8*9)$
161790825	$(-1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6-7)^*8-9)$	207532904	$1+23+4^*(5+6+7^8*9)$
161814135	$(-1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6-7)^*8+9)$	207533083	$1^*23+4^*(56+7^8*9)$
161935865	$(-1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6+7)^*8-9)$	207533084	$1+23+4^*(56+7^8*9)$
161959175	$(-1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6+7)^*8+9)$	207534340	$12^3-4^*(56-7^8*9)$
162040695	$(1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6-7)^*8-9)$	207534788	$12^3+4^*(56+7^8*9)$
162064041	$(1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6-7)^*8+9)$	212624892	$(-1-2)^3*(4-5^6*7^8*9)$
162185959	$(1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6+7)^*8-9)$	212625108	$(1+2)^3*(4+5^6*7^8*9)$
162209305	$(1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6+7)^*8+9)$	214156162	$(1-23)^*(4-5^6*7^8*9)$
162620691	$(-1+2^*(3^4(4^5-6)-7))^*(8+9)$	214156338	$(-1+23)^*(4+5^6*7^8*9)$
162620725	$(1+2^*(3^4(4^5-6)-7))^*(8+9)$	219651849	$1/2^*(3^4(4+5)^6+7^8*9)$
162621167	$(-1+2^*(3^4(4^5-6)+7))^*(8+9)$	223543296	$(1+2/3-4^5/6^7)^*8^9$
162621201	$(1+2^*(3^4(4^5-6)+7))^*(8+9)$	223696207	$(-1-2/3)^*(4-5^6(6-7)-8^9)$
164061996	$(-1+(2+3)^4(4+5)/6)^*7^8*9)$	223882348	$(1+23^*(4+5^6*7))^*8-9)$
164063004	$(1+(2+3)^4(4+5)/6)^*7^8*9)$	223882436	$-1-23^*(4-5^6*7)^*89$
164102448	$(1+2)/(3^4+5)^6(6+7-8-9)$	223882438	$1-23^*(4-5^6*7)^*89$
164296828	$1/-2+(3-(4-5)/6)^*7^8*9)$	223882526	$(1-23^*(4-5^6*7))^*89$
164296829	$1/2+(3-(4-5)/6)^*7^8*9)$	223890532	$-1-23^*(4-5^6*7^8*9)$
164531190	$(12+3)^*(-4+5^6*7^8*9)$	223890534	$1-23^*(4-5^6*7^8*9)$
164531310	$(12+3)^*(4+5^6*7^8*9)$	223890716	$-1+23^*(4+5^6*7^8*9)$
164607579	$(1+2)^*((3+4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	223890718	$1+23^*(4+5^6*7^8*9)$
168232527	$-12+3^*(4^4(5+6)+7^8*9)$	223898724	$(-1+23^*(4+5^6*7))^*89$
168232530	$(1+2)^*(-3+4^4(5+6)+7^8*9)$	223898812	$-1+23^*(4+5^6*7)^*89$
168232548	$(1+2)^*(3+4^4(5+6)+7^8*9)$	223898814	$1+23^*(4+5^6*7)^*89$
168232551	$12+3^*(4^4(5+6)+7^8*9)$	223898902	$(1+23^*(4+5^6*7))^*89$
182168343	$(-1+2/3^4-4^*(5^6-7)^*8)^*9$	226409976	$(-1+2/3^4-4^5)^*(6^7-8^9)$
182168361	$(1+2/3^4-4^*(5^6-7)^*8)^*9$	226454471	$(-1+2^3*3^4*5)^*(6^7-8-9)$
182331639	$(-1+2/3^4-4^*(5^6+7)^*8)^*9$	226467415	$(-1+2^3*3^4*5)^*(6^7+8-9)$
182331657	$(1+2/3^4-4^*(5^6+7)^*8)^*9$	226469033	$(-1+2^3*3^4*5)^*(6^7-8+9)$
184473356	$-12^*(3+4^*(5-6^7+8/9))$	226481977	$(-1+2^3*3^4*5)^*(6^7+8+9)$
184473428	$12^*(3-4^*(5-6^7+8/9))$	226526472	$(-1+2/3^4-4^5)^*(6^7+8^9)$
184473620	$-12+(3+45)^*6^7+8/9$	226747981	$-1+2^*(3^4*5^6+7-89)$
184473644	$12+(3+45)^*6^7+8/9$	226747983	$1+2^*(3^4*5^6+7-89)$
184473836	$-12^*(3-4^*(5+6^7+8/9))$	226748339	$1+2^*(3^4*5^6+7+89)$
184473908	$12^*(3+4^*(5+6^7+8/9))$	226969704	$(1+2/3^4-4^5)^*(6^7-8^9)$
184953036	$(-1+(23-4)^*5^6*7)^*89$	227014309	$(1+2^3*3^4*5)^*(6^7-8-9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
227027285	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8-9)$	268343603	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*567-8^{\wedge}9)$
227028096	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4*5)^*6^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}(-8-9)$	268371951	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*56*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
227028907	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-8+9)$	268371953	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*56*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
227041883	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8+9)$	268381185	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5*67-8^{\wedge}9)$
227086488	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}-4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8*9)$	268381187	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5*67-8^{\wedge}9)$
228062334	$(1+2)^*((3-4*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	268423791	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+67)-8^{\wedge}9)$
229042817	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4/5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8-9)$	268423793	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+67)-8^{\wedge}9)$
229602687	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4/5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8-9)$	268423931	$-1-2^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*67-8^{\wedge}9)$
230326893	$(-1+234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$	268423933	$1-2^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*67-8^{\wedge}9)$
230326901	$-1+234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)^*9$	268425271	$-1-2^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*67-8^{\wedge}9)$
230326903	$1+234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)^*9$	268425273	$1-2^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*67-8^{\wedge}9)$
230326911	$(1+234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$	268425411	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-67)+8^{\wedge}9)$
230360589	$(-1+234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$	268425413	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-67)+8^{\wedge}9)$
230360597	$-1+234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)^*9$	268426369	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*56+7-8^{\wedge}9)$
230360599	$1+234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)^*9$	268426371	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*56+7-8^{\wedge}9)$
230360607	$(1+234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$	268426397	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*56-7-8^{\wedge}9)$
230591572	$12^*(-3+4*(5/6/7^{\wedge}8-9))$	268426399	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*56-7-8^{\wedge}9)$
230591644	$12^*(3+4*(5/6/7^{\wedge}8-9))$	268433539	$1-2^*((3^{\wedge}4+56)^*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
230592364	$-12^*(3-4*5/(6/(7^{\wedge}8+9)))$	268434513	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5+67-8^{\wedge}9)$
230592508	$12^*(3+4*(5/(6/7^{\wedge}8+9)))$	268434781	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5-67-8^{\wedge}9)$
233473221	$1/2^*(3^{\wedge}4*(-5*6+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$	268436131	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5-67+8^{\wedge}9)$
233624904	$(1+23)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$	268436399	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5+67+8^{\wedge}9)$
233625096	$(1+23)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$	268437373	$-1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4+56)^*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
235064105	$-12+((3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5*6+7)/89$	268444513	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*56-7+8^{\wedge}9)$
235064129	$12+((3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5*6+7)/89$	268444515	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*56-7+8^{\wedge}9)$
237999983	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)*5^{\wedge}6*7)^*(8+9)$	268444541	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*56+7+8^{\wedge}9)$
238000017	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)*5^{\wedge}6*7)^*(8+9)$	268444543	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*56+7+8^{\wedge}9)$
241312412	$(1-23)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$	268445499	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-67)-8^{\wedge}9)$
241312588	$(-1+23)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$	268445501	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-67)-8^{\wedge}9)$
241780032	$12^{\wedge}3*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9)$	268445639	$-1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*67+8^{\wedge}9)$
241793856	$12^{\wedge}3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9)$	268445641	$1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*67+8^{\wedge}9)$
244206144	$12^{\wedge}3*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$	268446979	$-1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*67+8^{\wedge}9)$
244219968	$12^{\wedge}3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$	268446981	$1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*67+8^{\wedge}9)$
244994301	$(1+(2-3/4)^{\wedge}5)^*6^{\wedge}(-7+8+9)$	268447119	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+67)+8^{\wedge}9)$
247886416	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)/6/7^{\wedge}8-9)$	268447121	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+67)+8^{\wedge}9)$
247886470	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)/(6/7^{\wedge}8+9))$	268489725	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5*67+8^{\wedge}9)$
249039403	$-1/(2+3)+4/(5/6*7^{\wedge}8-9)^*9$	268489727	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*5*67+8^{\wedge}9)$
249261493	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3*(4+5)))^*(6/7-8+9)$	268498959	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*56*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
250192754	$(-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4/5+6))^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$	268498961	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*56*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
252280413	$(1+23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78))^*-9$	268527309	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*567+8^{\wedge}9)$
252280421	$-1-23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	268527310	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*567+8^{\wedge}9)$
252280423	$1-23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	268527311	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4*567+8^{\wedge}9)$
252280431	$(1-23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78))^*9$	268654137	$-1-2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
252281157	$-1-23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	268654139	$1-2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
252281159	$1-23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	268654273	$-1+2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
252281341	$-1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	268654275	$1+2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
252281343	$1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	269792687	$1/(2+3)-(4/5-6)^*7^{\wedge}8*9$
252282069	$(-1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78))^*9$	269999899	$-12+3^{\wedge}4-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7-89$
252282077	$-1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	269999923	$12+3^{\wedge}4-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7-89$
252282079	$1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	270000077	$-12+3^{\wedge}4-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7+89$
252282087	$(1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78))^*9$	270000101	$12+3^{\wedge}4-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7+89$
254313151	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4*5-6))/(7+8+9)$	272091864	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)+89)$
254803989	$12+(3+45)^{\wedge}(6+7-8)+9$	272094000	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)-89)$
255300564	$12*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7-89)$	272101584	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)+89)$
255302700	$12*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+89)$	272103720	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)+89)$
259413764	$-1-(2+3)^*(456-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	276686256	$-12^{\wedge}3/4*(56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$
259413765	$(1+2+3)^*(-456+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	276734640	$12^{\wedge}3/4*(56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
259413766	$1-(2+3)^*(456-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	278686192	$-1+23*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
259418324	$-1+(2+3)^*(456+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	278686194	$1+23*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
259418325	$(1+2+3)^*(456+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	280169010	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4/5*(6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
259418326	$1+(2+3)^*(456+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	280169064	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4/5*(6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
261722374	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4/5+6))^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$	282475222	$(-1-2)^{\wedge}3+(4-5-6)^{\wedge}(-7+8+9)$
262828036	$(-1+(23+4)*5^{\wedge}6*7)^*89$	282475276	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3+(4-5-6)^{\wedge}(-7+8+9)$
262828214	$(1+(23+4)*5^{\wedge}6*7)^*89$	288240031	$-1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4-56)^*7^{\wedge}8-9)$
263249904	$(1+23)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	288240033	$1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4-56)^*7^{\wedge}8-9)$
263250096	$(1+23)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	288240049	$-1-(2*3-456)^*7^{\wedge}8/9$
268216637	$-1-2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	288240051	$1-(2*3-456)^*7^{\wedge}8/9$
268216639	$1-2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	288240067	$-1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4-56)^*7^{\wedge}8+9)$
268216773	$-1+2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	288240069	$1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4-56)^*7^{\wedge}8+9)$
268216775	$1+2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	288458040	$(1+2)^*((3+4*5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
268343601	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4*567-8^{\wedge}9)$	288892884	$12*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7-89)$
268343602	$-1*2^*(3^{\wedge}4*567-8^{\wedge}9)$	288895020	$12*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7+89)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
294004681	$(1+2/3+4) * (5^* - 6+7^8*9)$	363179271	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (456-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
294005021	$(1+(2/3+4)) * (5^*6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	363181623	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4^*5^*6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
297464196	$(1+2^*(3+4/5)) * (6^*(7^{\wedge}8+9))$	363182059	$-12-(3+4) * (56-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
298539108	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5-6^{\wedge}7) * 89$	363182155	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4^*(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
298966788	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5-6^{\wedge}7*89)$	363182281	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3) * (4-5^*6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
298976508	$12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6^{\wedge}7*89)$	363182358	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4+5+6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
299404188	$12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6^{\wedge}7) * 89$	363182365	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4^*5-6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
302210835	$(-1-2) * (3^{\wedge}(4^*5-6)) * 7-8^{\wedge}9)$	363182414	$(1+2^*3) * (4-5-6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
302652052	$-1/2+(3+4) * 5/(6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$	363182512	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4-5-6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
302652053	$1/2+(3+4) * 5/(6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$	363182561	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3) * (4^*5-6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
303503970	$(-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4) * (5^{\wedge}6 * (7+8) - 9)$	363182568	$(1+2^*3) * (4+5+6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
303527280	$(-1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4) * (5^{\wedge}6 * (7+8) + 9)$	363182645	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4-5^*6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
303749943	$(1+(2^{\wedge}(3^*4) - (5^*6)^{\wedge}7) / 8) / -9$	363182771	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3) * (4^*(5+6) + 7^{\wedge}8*9)$
303750057	$(1+(2^{\wedge}(3^*4) + (5^*6)^{\wedge}7) / 8) / 9$	363182867	$12+(3+4) * (56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
303972702	$(1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4) * (5^{\wedge}6 * (7+8) - 9)$	363183303	$(1+2^*3) * (4^*5^*6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
303996048	$(1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4) * (5^{\wedge}6 * (7+8) + 9)$	363185655	$(1+2^*3) * (456+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
304570351	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3+4+5) * 6^{\wedge}7) * (8+9)$	363189589	$(1+2^*3) * (4^{\wedge}5-6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
304570385	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3+4+5) * 6^{\wedge}7) * (8+9)$	363189673	$(1+2^*3) * (4^{\wedge}5+6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
311296517	$-1-2^*3^*(456-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	363193215	$(1+2^*3) * ((4^{\wedge}5/6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
311296518	$(-1-2-3) * (456-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	363225471	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3) * (4^{\wedge}5^*6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
311296519	$1-2^*3^*(456-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	363291810	$(1+2^*3) * (-4+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
311301989	$-1+2^*3^*(456+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	363291866	$(1+2^*3) * (4+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
311301990	$(1+2+3) * (456+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	363619963	$(1+2^*3) * (4/5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
311301991	$1+2^*3^*(456+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	364166810	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4-(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
319946455	$1/-2+(3+4-5/6) * 7^{\wedge}8*9$	364166866	$(1+2^*3) * (4+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
319946456	$1/2+(3+4-5/6) * 7^{\wedge}8*9$	366902550	$(1+2^*3) * ((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
322825832	$12^*(3-45) * (6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	368943808	$12^*(3+45) * (-6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
322831880	$-12^*(3-45) * (6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	368950720	$12^*(3+45) * (6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
326637184	$(1+2/(3+4) * 5) * (6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	377552896	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3^*4) * (5^{\wedge}6-7)) * 8^{\wedge}9$
330429696	$(-1-2) * ((3^{\wedge}4+5) * 6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$	378011648	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(-3^*4) * (5^{\wedge}6+7)) * 8^{\wedge}9$
332859267	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3 * (-4+5^{\wedge}6 * 789)$	382941495	$(-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5) * (6^{\wedge}7-8)) * 9$
332859483	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3 * (4+5^{\wedge}6 * 789)$	382941513	$(1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5) * (6^{\wedge}7-8)) * 9$
333822335	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4^{\wedge}(5+6) - 7^{\wedge}8*9)$	382952295	$(-1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4-5) * 6^{\wedge}7-8)) * 9$
334627521	$(-1-2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * (5+6^{\wedge}7) - 8^{\wedge}9)$	382952313	$(1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4-5) * 6^{\wedge}7-8)) * 9$
334629951	$(1+2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * (5-6^{\wedge}7) + 8^{\wedge}9)$	382952583	$(-1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4-5) * 6^{\wedge}7+8)) * 9$
338827776	$(-1-2) * ((3^{\wedge}4-5) * 6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$	382952601	$(1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4-5) * 6^{\wedge}7+8)) * 9$
340120269	$(1+2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * (5^*6^{\wedge}7-8) - 9)$	382963383	$(-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5) * (6^{\wedge}7+8)) * 9$
340120323	$(1+2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * (5^*6^{\wedge}7-8) + 9)$	382963401	$(1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5) * (6^{\wedge}7+8)) * 9$
340122189	$(1+2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * 5^*6^{\wedge}7-8-9)$	383936346	$(1+2) * ((3^{\wedge}4/5+6) * (7^{\wedge}8+9))$
340122237	$(1+2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * 5^*6^{\wedge}7+8-9)$	385471455	$-12-3^{\wedge}4 * (5-6^{\wedge}7 * (8+9))$
340122243	$(1+2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * 5^*6^{\wedge}7-8+9)$	385471479	$12-3^{\wedge}4 * (5-6^{\wedge}7 * (8+9))$
340122291	$(1+2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * 5^*6^{\wedge}7+8+9)$	385472265	$-12+3^{\wedge}4 * (5+6^{\wedge}7 * (8+9))$
340124157	$(1+2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * (5^*6^{\wedge}7+8) - 9)$	385472289	$12+3^{\wedge}4 * (5+6^{\wedge}7 * (8+9))$
340124211	$(1+2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * (5^*6^{\wedge}7+8) + 9)$	386201085	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5-6+7) / 8-9)$
345887763	$(1+2^{\wedge}3) * (4-5/6/7^{\wedge}8) * -9$	386201123	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5-6+7) / 8+9)$
345887781	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4-5/6/7^{\wedge}8) * 9$	392006432	$12^*(-3+(45+6) * 7^{\wedge}8/9)$
345887997	$(1+2^*(3-4^*5/6/7^{\wedge}8)) * -9$	392006504	$12^*(3+(45+6) * 7^{\wedge}8/9)$
345888123	$(1+2^*(3+4^*5/6/7^{\wedge}8)) * 9$	392542591	$(1+2^*3) * (4^{\wedge}(5+6) + 7^{\wedge}8*9)$
345888339	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3) * (4+5/6/7^{\wedge}8) * 9$	394312491	$(1+2) * ((3+4/5) * (6^*7^{\wedge}8+9))$
345888357	$(1+2^{\wedge}3) * (4+5/6/7^{\wedge}8) * 9$	394874991	$(-1+(2+34) * 5^{\wedge}6 * 78) * 9$
345990236	$(12+3^*(45^{\wedge}6+7) / 8) / 9$	394875009	$(1+(2+34) * 5^{\wedge}6 * 78) * 9$
347649615	$-12+3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	395507812	$-1/2+3^{\wedge}4-4^*5/6^*(7+8)^{\wedge}9$
347649618	$(1+2) * (-3+(4^*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	395507813	$1/2+3^{\wedge}4-4^*5/6^*(7+8)^{\wedge}9$
347649636	$(1+2) * (3+(4^*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	395538255	$(-1+(2^*3^{\wedge}4-5) * (6^{\wedge}7-8)) * 9$
347649639	$12+3^*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	395538273	$(1+(2^*3^{\wedge}4-5) * (6^{\wedge}7-8)) * 9$
350437411	$(-1+(2+34) * 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 89$	395560863	$(-1+(2^*3^{\wedge}4-5) * (6^{\wedge}7+8)) * 9$
350437589	$(1+(2+34) * 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 89$	395560881	$(1+(2^*3^{\wedge}4-5) * (6^{\wedge}7+8)) * 9$
351562491	$(-1+(2+3) * 4/5^{\wedge}(6-7-8)) * 9$	398443776	$(-1-2) * ((3^{\wedge}4-4+5) * 6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$
351562509	$(1+(2+3) * 4/5^{\wedge}(6-7-8)) * 9$	398464512	$(1+2) * ((3^{\wedge}4-4+5) * 6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$
352805821	$-1/(2+3) + (4/5+6) * 7^{\wedge}8*9$	398715684	$(-1-2) * (3^*4/5^{\wedge}6-7-8^{\wedge}9)$
359462376	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * ((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	398854608	$(-1-2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6+7) - 8^{\wedge}9)$
362198060	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4+(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8) * 9)$	398858010	$(-1-2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6-7) - 8^{\wedge}9)$
362198116	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (-4+(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8) * 9)$	401340672	$-12-3^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6 * 7-8^{\wedge}9)$
362387884	$-1/2+3^{\wedge}4/(5^*6) * (7+8^{\wedge}9)$	401340675	$(-1-2) * (3+4^*5^{\wedge}6 * 7-8^{\wedge}9)$
362387885	$1/2+3^{\wedge}4/(5^*6/(7+8^{\wedge}9))$	401340693	$(1+2) * (3-4^*5^{\wedge}6 * 7+8^{\wedge}9)$
362744963	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4^*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	401340696	$12-3^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6 * 7-8^{\wedge}9)$
363073060	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	401668773	$(-1-2) * (3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6 * 7) - 8^{\wedge}9)$
363073116	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (-4+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	401668845	$(1+2) * (3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6 * 7) + 8^{\wedge}9)$
363139455	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4^{\wedge}5^*6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	401770464	$12^*(3^{\wedge}(4^*5-6) * 7+89)$
363171711	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4^{\wedge}5/6-7^{\wedge}8) * 9$	401812161	$(-1-2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * 5+6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$
363175253	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4^{\wedge}5+6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	401814591	$(1+2) * (3^{\wedge}4 * 5-6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$
363175337	$(1-2^{\wedge}3) * (4^{\wedge}5-6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	402323358	$(-1-2) * ((3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6) * 7-8^{\wedge}9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
402324816	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+5^6*7-8^9)$	402981345	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6*7+8^9)$
402325023	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+5^6*7-8^9)$	402981552	$(1+2)^*(3^4+5^6*7+8^9)$
402325035	$-12-3^*(4+5^6*7-8^9)$	402983010	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5^6)*7+8^9)$
402325083	$12+3^*(4-5^6*7+8^9)$	403491777	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5-6^7-8^9)$
402325095	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6*7+8^9)$	403494207	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5+6^7+8^9)$
402325302	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6*7+8^9)$	403637523	$(1+2)^*(3^*(4+5^6*7)+8^9)$
402326760	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5^6)*7+8^9)$	403637595	$(1+2)^*(3^*(4+5^6*7)+8^9)$
402515403	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*567-8^9)$	403965675	$(-1-2)^*(3-4^5*6*7-8^9)$
402601344	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-4^5*6^7-8^9)$	403965693	$(1+2)^*(3+4^5*6^7+8^9)$
402602154	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^6*7-8^9)$	403965696	$12+3^*(4^5*6^7+8^9)$
402634473	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5+6)*7-8^9)$	406418470	$1/-2+(3+4+5/6)*7^8*9$
402637389	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^*(6+7)-8^9)$	406418471	$1/2+(3+4+5/6)^*(7^8*9)$
402641763	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5+6*7)-8^9)$	406448358	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7)+8^9)$
402642348	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5)*6*7-8^9)$	406451760	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5^6+7)+8^9)$
402644193	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5-6*7)+8^9)$	406590684	$(1+2)^*(3^4/5^6-6*7+8^9)$
402644553	$(-1-2)^*((3^4*5+6)*7-8^9)$	406841856	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-4-5)*6^7-8^9)$
402644805	$(-1-2)^*((3^4*5-6)*7-8^9)$	406862592	$(1+2)^*((3^4-4+5)*6^7+8^9)$
402645873	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^6*7-8^9)$	407346816	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4^5*(5*6)^7-8^9)$
402645915	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^6*7-8^9)$	408127725	$(-1-2*3^4*(5-6^7+8))^9$
402647595	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7)-8^9)$	408127743	$(1-2*3^4*(5-6^7+8))^9$
402648810	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5+6+7)-8^9)$	408139245	$(-1-2*(3^4*(5-6^7+8))^9$
402649830	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5)^*(6+7)-8^9)$	408139263	$(1-2*(3^4*(5-6^7+8))^9$
402650220	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-5)^*(6+7)-8^9)$	408139533	$(-1-2*(3^4*(5-6^7-8))^9$
402650490	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5+6)+7-8^9)$	408139551	$(1-2*(3^4*(5-6^7-8))^9$
402650532	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5+6)-7-8^9)$	408142305	$(-1+2*3^4*(5+6^7-8))^9$
402650853	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5^6)*7-8^9)$	408142323	$(1+2*3^4*(5+6^7-8))^9$
402651252	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5+6)*7-8^9)$	408151053	$(-1-2*3^4*(5-6^7-8))^9$
402651615	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5)*6+7-8^9)$	408151071	$(1-2*3^4*(5-6^7-8))^9$
402651657	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5)*6-7-8^9)$	408153825	$(-1+2*(3^4*(5+6^7-8))^9$
402651714	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-5-6)*7-8^9)$	408153843	$(1+2*(3^4*(5+6^7-8))^9$
402651843	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5+6*7-8^9)$	408154113	$(-1+2*(3^4*(5+6^7+8))^9$
402651930	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5+6+7-8^9)$	408154131	$(1+2*(3^4*(5+6^7+8))^9$
402651966	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5-6+7-8^9)$	408165633	$(-1+2*3^4*(5+6^7+8))^9$
402651969	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5/(6-7)+8^9)$	408165651	$(1+2*3^4*(5+6^7+8))^9$
402652212	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5+6-7)-8^9)$	412760396	$(12-3/45)^6*(7^8+9)$
402652883	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5)/-6*7+8^9)$	415062023	$-1-2^3*(456-7^8*9)$
402652918	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5)/-6*7+8^9)$	415062024	$1*2^3*(-456+7^8*9)$
402653450	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5)/6*7+8^9)$	415062025	$1-2^3*(456-7^8*9)$
402653485	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5)/6*7+8^9)$	415065217	$-1-2*(3+4*(56-7^8*9))$
402654156	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5+6-7)+8^9)$	415065219	$1-2*(3+4*(56-7^8*9))$
402654399	$(1+2)^*(3^4/5^6(6-7)+8^9)$	415065229	$-1+2*(3-4*(56-7^8*9))$
402654402	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5-6+7+8^9)$	415066115	$1-2*(3-4*(56+7^8*9))$
402654438	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5+6+7+8^9)$	415066125	$-1+2*(3+4*(56+7^8*9))$
402654525	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5+6*7+8^9)$	415066127	$1+2*(3+4*(56+7^8*9))$
402654654	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5-6)*7+8^9)$	415069319	$-1+2^3*(456+7^8*9)$
402654711	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5)*6-7+8^9)$	415069320	$1*2^3*(456+7^8*9)$
402654753	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5)*6+7+8^9)$	415069321	$1+2^3*(456+7^8*9)$
402655116	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5+6)*7+8^9)$	417372244	$(12+3/45)^*(6*(7^8+9))$
402655515	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5^6)*7+8^9)$	419389441	$(1-(2^3)^4*5)^{(-6+7-8+9)}$
402655836	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5+6)-7+8^9)$	419471361	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^{(-6+7-8+9)}$
402655878	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5+6)+7+8^9)$	420350373	$(1+2)^*(3/(4^5))^{(-6-7^8*9)}$
402656148	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5)^*(6+7)+8^9)$	420731775	$(-1+(2^3*4+5)^*(6^7-8))^9$
402656538	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5)^*(6+7)+8^9)$	420731793	$(1+(2^3*4+5)^*(6^7-8))^9$
402657558	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5+6+7)+8^9)$	420755823	$(-1+(2^3*4+5)^*(6^7+8))^9$
402658773	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7)+8^9)$	420755841	$(1+(2^3*4+5)^*(6^7+8))^9$
402660453	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5^6*7+8^9)$	421653926	$-1+(2^3-3)^4*5^6*7-8^9$
402660495	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5^6+7+8^9)$	421653928	$1+(2^3-3)^4*5^6*7-8^9$
402661563	$(1+2)^*((3^4*5-6)*7+8^9)$	421654104	$-1+(2^3-3)^4*5^6*7+8^9$
402661815	$(1+2)^*((3^4*5+6)*7+8^9)$	421654106	$1+(2^3-3)^4*5^6*7+8^9$
402662175	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5^6+7)+8^9)$	433340775	$(-1+2*((3^4+5)*6^7-8))^9$
402664020	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5)*6*7+8^9)$	433340793	$(1+2*((3^4+5)*6^7-8))^9$
402664605	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5+6*7)+8^9)$	433341063	$(-1+2*((3^4+5)*6^7+8))^9$
402668979	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5*(6+7)+8^9)$	433341081	$(1+2*((3^4+5)*6^7+8))^9$
402671895	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5+6)*7+8^9)$	441458669	$-1+2*(3^4*5^6-7^8*9)$
402704214	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5^6*7+8^9)$	441458671	$1+2*(3^4*5^6-7^8*9)$
402705024	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4^5*6^7+8^9)$	446195649	$(1+2*(3+4/5))^*(6+7^8*9)$
402790965	$(1+2)^*(3^4*567+8^9)$	446410440	$(1+2/3)/((4+5)^{-6/7/8/9})$
402979608	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-5^6)*7-8^9)$	447595785	$(-1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7-8^9)$
402981066	$(1+2)^*(-3^4+5^6*7+8^9)$	447814391	$(1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7-8^9)$
402981273	$(1+2)^*(-3^4+5^6*7+8^9)$	447821010	$(-1+2^3(3^4))^*(5^6*7-8^9)$
402981285	$-12-3^*(4-5^6*7-8^9)$	447886530	$(-1+2^3(3^4))^*(5^6*7+8-9)$
402981333	$12+3^*(4+5^6*7+8^9)$	447886985	$(-1+2^3(3^4))^*(5^6*7-8/9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
447894265	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8/9)$	536433389	$1*-23-4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
447894720	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8+9)$	536433390	$1-23-4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
447960240	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9)$	536433397	$-12-3-4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
448039726	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8-9)$	536433427	$12+3-4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
448105278	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8-9)$	536433434	$-1+23-4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
448113472	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8+9)$	536433435	$1*23-4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
448179024	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9)$	536433436	$1+23-4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
448185465	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8*9)$	537308388	$-1-23+4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
448404359	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8*9)$	537308389	$1*-23+4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
449599039	$(1-2*3^{\wedge}(4*5-6))^*(-7*8+9)$	537308390	$1-23+4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
449599133	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}(-4*5+6))^*(7*8-9)$	537308397	$-12-3+4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
449654477	$-1+2*(345+6)*7^{\wedge}8/9$	537308427	$12+3+4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
449654479	$1+2*(345+6)*7^{\wedge}8/9$	537308434	$-1+23+4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
461184044	$12*(-3+(4+56)*7^{\wedge}8/9)$	537308435	$1*23+4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
461184116	$12*(3+(4+56)*7^{\wedge}8/9)$	537308436	$1+23+4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
465683220	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)*9)$	544185837	$(-1-2)*3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)*8+9$
465683292	$(1+2^{\wedge}3)^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)*9)$	544185891	$(-1-2)*3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)*8-9$
466478592	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	544194342	$(-1-2)*3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)*8+9$
466943604	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(56-7^{\wedge}8+9)$	544194396	$(-1-2)*3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)*8-9$
466943628	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(56-7^{\wedge}8+9)$	544196772	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)*8-9$
466945062	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(56-7^{\wedge}8-9)$	544196826	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)*8+9$
466945086	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(56-7^{\wedge}8-9)$	544205277	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)*8-9$
466948084	$-1/2-3^{\wedge}4*(5/6-7^{\wedge}8+9)$	544205331	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)*8+9$
466948085	$1/2-3^{\wedge}4*(5/6-7^{\wedge}8+9)$	545994384	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7*8-9)$
466948219	$-1/2+3^{\wedge}4*(5/6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	546005616	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7*8+9)$
466948220	$1/2+3^{\wedge}4*(5/6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	547744366	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7*8-9)$
466949542	$-1/2-3^{\wedge}4*(5/6-7^{\wedge}8-9)$	547755634	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7*8+9)$
466949543	$1/2-3^{\wedge}4*(5/6-7^{\wedge}8-9)$	552136625	$(1+2/3)*((4+(5+6)^{\wedge}7)*(8+9))$
466949677	$-1/2+3^{\wedge}4*(5/6+7^{\wedge}8+9)$	569173056	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}(4*5-6))^*7)*(-8-9)$
466949678	$1/2+3^{\wedge}4*(5/6+7^{\wedge}8+9)$	569173090	$(1-(2-3^{\wedge}(4*5-6))^*7)*(8+9)$
466952676	$-12+3^{\wedge}4*(56+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	569173532	$(-1+(2+3^{\wedge}(4*5-6))^*7)*(8+9)$
466952700	$12+3^{\wedge}4*(56+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	569173566	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}(4*5-6))^*7)*(8+9)$
466954134	$-12+3^{\wedge}4*(56+7^{\wedge}8+9)$	569434232	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*(5+6))^*7^{\wedge}8)/-9$
466954158	$12+3^{\wedge}4*(56+7^{\wedge}8+9)$	570696777	$(-1+(2-(3+4)^{\wedge}5)*6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$
467246796	$-12*(3-4/5^{\wedge}6-7)*89$	570715064	$-1-234+(5+6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$
467250036	$12*(3+4/5^{\wedge}6-7)*89$	570715066	$1-234+(5+6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$
469763263	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6+7/8^{\wedge}9)$	570715532	$-1+234+(5+6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$
470676417	$(-1-2)*3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)-8^{\wedge}9$	570715534	$1+234+(5+6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$
470678847	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)+8^{\wedge}9$	570733821	$(-1+(2+(3+4)^{\wedge}5)*6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$
474609348	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4/5^{\wedge}(6-7-8)-9$	571996366	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4*(5+6))^*7^{\wedge}8)/9$
474609402	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4/5^{\wedge}(6-7-8)+9$	573935607	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7*8))^*9$
474876672	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	573935625	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7*8))^*9$
492890485	$1/-2+3*(4-5/6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$	575447031	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7-8))^*9$
492890486	$1/2+3*(4-5/6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$	575447049	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7-8))^*9$
495772241	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*(5-6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$	575963127	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7-8))^*9$
495772757	$(1+2/(3/4/5))^*(6*7^{\wedge}8-9)$	575963145	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7-8))^*9$
495773015	$(1+2/(3/4/5))^*(6*7^{\wedge}8+9)$	575967735	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7/8))^*9$
495773531	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*(5+6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$	575967753	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7/8))^*9$
498078900	$12*(3+4/5*(6+7^{\wedge}8*9))$	576032247	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7/8))^*9$
503095533	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)*7+8^{\wedge}9$	576032265	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7/8))^*9$
510603237	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7*8-9)$	576036855	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7+8))^*9$
510603291	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7*8+9)$	576036873	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7+8))^*9$
511608825	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)*8-9)$	576552951	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7+8))^*9$
511682535	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)*8+9)$	576552969	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7+8))^*9$
511858695	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)*8-9)$	577787877	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*6^{\wedge}7*8-9)$
511932441	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)*8+9)$	577787931	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*6^{\wedge}7*8+9)$
512067465	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)*8-9)$	578064375	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7*8))^*9$
512141175	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)*8+9)$	578064393	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7*8))^*9$
512317559	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)*8-9)$	579362500	$-1/2+(3*4-5/6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$
512391305	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)*8+9)$	579362501	$1/2+(3*4-5/6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$
516552228	$12*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)-78)*9$	591468651	$(1+2)*((3+4/5)*(6+7^{\wedge}8*9))$
518831963	$1-2*(34+5*(6-7^{\wedge}8*9))$	599757294	$(1+2)*((3+4*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
518832217	$-1+2*(34+5*(6+7^{\wedge}8*9))$	602653941	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)*7-8))^*-9$
518832486	$12*(-3+(4+5/6/7^{\wedge}8)*9)$	602654247	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)*7+8))^*9$
524591977	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4)/(5/(6-7^{\wedge}8/9))$	607499991	$(-1+2/3^{\wedge}4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7/8)^*9$
524601805	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}4))/(5/(6+7^{\wedge}8/9))$	607500009	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7/8)^*9$
526500036	$12*(3+4/5^{\wedge}6-7*8*9)$	615189366	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
529475129	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*5)^{\wedge}6/(7-8)+9$	615189384	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
531727659	$-1-2*(34^{\wedge}5-6*7^{\wedge}8*9)$	615279366	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
531727661	$1-2*(34^{\wedge}5-6*7^{\wedge}8*9)$	615279384	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
533411731	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*5)^{\wedge}6/(7-8)+9$	615848472	$-12*(3+(4*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)*9)$
536433388	$-1-23-4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	615848544	$12*(3-(4*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)*9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
619139699	$(12-3/45)*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	752306530	$-1/2+3*(4+5/6)*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
621785905	$(1-2/3^{\wedge}(-4*5+6))*(7-8^*9)$	752306531	$1/2+3*(4+5/6)*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
621786035	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}(-4*5+6))*(7*8+9)$	755709023	$(1-2*3^{\wedge}(4*5-6))*(7-8^*9)$
622108620	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*5-56+7^{\wedge}8/9)^*9$	755709181	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}(-4*5+6))*(7+8^*9)$
622544076	$-12*3^{\wedge}4*(56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	755846208	$12^{\wedge}3*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$
622591209	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6/7^{\wedge}8-8))^*9$	756153792	$12^{\wedge}3*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$
622591227	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6/7^{\wedge}8-8))^*9$	761186917	$(1+(2/3+4))*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
622593804	$12*((-3-4)*56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	762939453	$(-1+(2+3)^{\wedge}(4*5-6))/(7-8+9)$
622595052	$12*((-3-45)*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	767871582	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4)/5)*(-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
622595232	$12*(-3-45*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	770929957	$(-1-2*3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7))^*(8+9)$
622595304	$12*(3-45*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	770929991	$(1-2*3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7))^*(8+9)$
622595484	$12*((3-45)*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	770957497	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7))^*(8+9)$
622596636	$12*(3*(4-56)+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	770957531	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7))^*(8+9)$
622596864	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	778244775	$(12+3)*(-4*5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
622599171	$-12*(3/4-56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	778247370	$(12+3)*(-45-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
622600152	$12*(3^{\wedge}4+56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	778247550	$(12+3)*(-45+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
622600380	$12*(-3*(4-56)+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	778247802	$(1+2)*(-3^{\wedge}4-5*(6-7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
622601532	$12*((-3+45)*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	778248009	$(1+2)*3*(3^{\wedge}4-5*(6-7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
622601712	$12*(-3+45*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	778248021	$-12-3*(4+5*(6-7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
622601784	$12*(3+45*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	778248069	$12+3*(4-5*(6-7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
622601964	$12*((3+45)*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	778248201	$-12-3*(4-5*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
622603212	$12*((3+45)*56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	778248249	$12+3*(4+5*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
622605789	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6/7^{\wedge}8-8))^*9$	778248261	$(1+2)*3*(4+5*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
622605807	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6/7^{\wedge}8-8))^*9$	778248468	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4+5*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
622652940	$12*3^{\wedge}4*(56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	778248720	$(12+3)*(45-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
623088396	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*56+7^{\wedge}8/9)^*9$	778248900	$(12+3)*(45+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
626057461	$(12+3/45)*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	778251495	$(12+3)*(4*5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
629348472	$12*(-3+(4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	782936787	$-1/2+(3+4)*5/(6/(7+8^{\wedge}9))$
629348544	$12*(3+(4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	782936788	$1/2+(3+4)*5/(6/(7+8^{\wedge}9))$
634122170	$(1-23)*45*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	789776492	$-12+(3^{\wedge}4+56)*7^{\wedge}8-9$
634134050	$(1-23)*45*(-6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	789776516	$12+(3^{\wedge}4+56)*7^{\wedge}8-9$
637006279	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5*6^{\wedge}7-8))/9$	789778958	$-12+(3^{\wedge}4+56)*7^{\wedge}8-9$
637013561	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5*6^{\wedge}7+8))/9$	789778982	$12+(3^{\wedge}4+56)*7^{\wedge}8-9$
637806208	$12^{\wedge}3(3+4)/(5/(6^{\wedge}7+89))^*9$	794738287	$(-1+(2*3^{\wedge}4+5)*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$
644245061	$1/(2+3)-4/(5/6)*(7-8^{\wedge}9)$	794738321	$(1+(2*3^{\wedge}4+5)*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$
645988352	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*8^{\wedge}9$	809999784	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4-4/(5*6)^{\wedge}7-8^*9$
646447104	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6+7))^*8^{\wedge}9$	809999949	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7-8-9$
648991505	$-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	809999997	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7+8-9$
648991507	$1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	810000003	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7-8+9$
650139823	$(1+2/3+4)*((-5-6)^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	810000051	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7+8+9$
662945904	$-1-23*45*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	810000216	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4-4/(5*6)^{\wedge}7+8^*9$
662945905	$1-23*45*(-6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	811182463	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3)*((4*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
662945906	$1-23*45*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	850885956	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)/5)*6*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$
662958324	$-1+23*45*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	879710006	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)/(5/6))^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$
662958325	$1+23*45*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	882013601	$1/2*34*(-56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
662958326	$1+23*45*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	882015505	$1/2*34*(56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
665834515	$1/-2+(3*4+5/6)*7^{\wedge}8^*9$	888888889	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6*(-6+7+8))/9$
665834516	$1/2+(3*4+5/6)*7^{\wedge}8^*9$	891239626	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)/(5/6))^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$
688746519	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)-7)*8)^*9$	899307785	$-1-234*(5-6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
688746537	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)-7)*8)^*9$	899307786	$-1*234*(5-6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
688748535	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)+7)*8)^*9$	899307787	$1-234*(5-6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
688748553	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)+7)*8)^*9$	899310125	$-1+234*(5+6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
691769640	$(-1-23)*45*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	920063676	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)/5)*(6*(7^{\wedge}8+9))$
691782600	$(1+23)*45*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	933151266	$(-1-2)*((3*4)^{\wedge}5-6/7^{\wedge}8-9)$
698844915	$(1+2/3)/((4+5)^{\wedge}6/789)$	933838713	$(1+2)*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
704642568	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3+4*5)/6)*7*8^*9$	933847341	$(-1-2)*((3+4)^{\wedge}5-6*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
704643576	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4*5)/6)*7*8^*9$	933888546	$(1+2)*3*(3^{\wedge}4+5+6*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
713469355	$-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5+6*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	933888671	$-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*(56-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
716416857	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)*6^{\wedge}7/8-9$	933888673	$1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*(56-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
716486823	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)*6^{\wedge}7/8-9$	933888707	$-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*(56-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
716785479	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)*6^{\wedge}7/8+9$	933888709	$1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*(56-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
716855481	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)*6^{\wedge}7/8+9$	933894678	$-12-3*(4^{\wedge}5-6*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
723354607	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$	933894702	$12-3*(4^{\wedge}5-6*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
723354641	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$	933896754	$(1-23+4)*(56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
731649627	$(1+2)*3/(4*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	933897504	$(-1-2)*3^{\wedge}4+5-6*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
736740792	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4/5)*6^{\wedge}7/8)^*9$	933897534	$(-1-2)*3^{\wedge}4-5-6*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
736740810	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4/5)*6^{\wedge}7/8)^*9$	933897657	$(-1-2)*((3+4)*5-6/7^{\wedge}8-9)$
742775424	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	933897867	$(1+2)*((3+4)*5+6/7^{\wedge}8-9)$
743659243	$(1+2/(3/4/5))*(-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	933897990	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4-5+6*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
743659415	$(1+2/(3/4/5))*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	933898020	$(1+2)*3^{\wedge}4+5+6*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
747149167	$(-1+(2*3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$	933898770	$(1-23+4)*(-56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
747149201	$(1+(2*3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$	933900822	$-12+3*(4^{\wedge}5+6*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
933906815	$-1+2*(3^4*(56+7^8)-9)$	1106945472	$12^3*(4+56+7^8/9)$
933906817	$1+2*(3^4*(56+7^8)-9)$	1107228864	$12^3*(4*56+7^8/9)$
933906851	$-1+2*(3^4*(56+7^8)+9)$	1107308352	$12^3*(45*6+7^8/9)$
933906853	$1+2*(3^4*(56+7^8)+9)$	1114914254	$(-1+2/(3^4-4*5/6))^*(7^8+9)$
933906978	$(1+2)*(3/4^5-5+6*7^8*9)$	1124134088	$-1+234*(5/6/7^8-8-9)$
933948183	$(1+2)*((3+4)^5+5+6*7^8*9)$	1124134089	$1*234*(5/6/7^8-8-9)$
933956811	$(1+2)*(3^4(4+5)+6*7^8*9)$	1124134090	$1+234*(5/6/7^8-8-9)$
934644258	$(1+2)*((3^4)^5+5+6/7^8-8*9)$	1124138300	$-1+234*(5/6/7^8-8+9)$
936461596	$(1-2^3)*(4*5^6*7-8^9)$	1124138301	$1*234*(5/(6/7^8)+9)$
938758443	$(1-2^3)*(4+5^6*7-8^9)$	1124138302	$1+234*(5/(6/7^8)+9)$
938758499	$(1+2^3)*(4-5^6*7+8^9)$	1126443874	$(1+2/(3^4-4*5/6))^*(7^8+9)$
939519548	$-12-3^4*56+7^8*9$	1133113345	$(-1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7^8-9)$
939519572	$12-3^4*56+7^8*9$	1133136655	$(-1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7^8+9)$
939528620	$-12+3^4*56+7^8*9$	1134863327	$(1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7^8-9)$
939528644	$12+3^4*56+7^8*9$	1134886673	$(1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7^8+9)$
940289693	$(1-2^3)*(4-5^6*7-8^9)$	1135655159	$(-12^3-45)^*(6-7^8/9)$
940289749	$(1+2^3)*(4+5^6*7+8^9)$	1135676435	$(12^3+45)^*(6+7^8/9)$
942586596	$(-1+2^3)*(4*5^6*7+8^9)$	1138346605	$(1-2*3^4(4*5-6)^7)^*(-8-9)$
944273412	$(1+(2+3^4/5)^*(6-7^8))^*-9$	1138346639	$(1+2/3^4(-4*5+6)^7)^*(8+9)$
944273430	$(1-(2+3^4/5)^*(6-7^8))^*9$	1141425670	$(1-23)^*(4*56-7^8*9)$
945074417	$1/2*((3+4)^5)^6+7^8*9$	1141429278	$(1-23)^*(4+56-7^8*9)$
955468224	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5)^6*(7+8-9)$	1141429454	$(-1+23)^*(4-56+7^8*9)$
955561536	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^6*(7+8-9)$	1141429476	$(1-23)^*(45+6-7^8*9)$
959728770	$(-1+2^3(3^4))^*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$	1141429740	$(1-23)^*(45-6-7^8*9)$
959802480	$(-1+2^3(3^4))^*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$	1141431456	$(-1+23)^*(45-6+7^8*9)$
960197502	$(1+2^3(3^4))^*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$	1141431720	$(-1+23)^*(45+6+7^8*9)$
960271248	$(1+2^3(3^4))^*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$	1141431742	$(1-23)^*(4-56-7^8*9)$
985779906	$-1-(23-4)^*(56-7^8*9)$	1141431918	$(-1+23)^*(4+56+7^8*9)$
985779908	$1-(23-4)^*(56-7^8*9)$	1141435526	$(-1+23)^*(4*56+7^8*9)$
985782034	$-1+(23-4)^*(56+7^8*9)$	1155266421	$(1+2*3^4/5)^*(6*7^8+9)$
985782036	$1+(23-4)^*(56+7^8*9)$	1162259888	$-1+2*((3^4)^5/6-789)$
1006611840	$(1+2)*((3*(4+5))^6-7^8*9)$	1162260252	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5+(6-7-8)^9)$
1015298847	$(1+(2-3^4*5)^*(6^7-8))^*-9$	1162260677	$-1+2*(3^4)^5/6-789$
1015298865	$(1-(2-3^4*5)^*(6^7-8))^*9$	1162262255	$-1+2*(3^4)^5/6+789$
1015356879	$(1+(2-3^4*5)^*(6^7+8))^*-9$	1162262682	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5-(6-7-8)^9)$
1015356897	$(1-(2-3^4*5)^*(6^7+8))^*9$	1162263044	$-1+2*((3^4)^5/6+789)$
1017252604	$(-1+(2+3)^4(4*5-6))/(7+8-9)$	1162263045	$1*2*((3^4)^5/6+789)$
1025376255	$(-1+(2+3^4*5)^*(6^7-8))^*9$	1162263046	$1+2*((3^4)^5/6+789)$
1025376273	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^*(6^7-8))^*9$	1167372336	$-1/(2/(3-45*(6+7^8*9)))$
1025434863	$(-1+(2+3^4*5)^*(6^7+8))^*9$	1169230140	$(1+2/3)^*(4*(5+6)^7-8)^*9$
1025434881	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^*(6^7+8))^*9$	1181090663	$-1-23*((4+5)^6-7^8*9)$
1033121277	$(1+2)*(3^4(4*(5+6-7))^8-9)$	1181090665	$1-23*((4+5)^6-7^8*9)$
1033121331	$(1+2)*(3^4(4*(5+6-7))^8+9)$	1184616252	$12*3^4*(5^6*78-9)$
1037654460	$12*3^4*45*(-6+7^8/9)$	1184633748	$12*3^4*(5^6*78+9)$
1037664057	$1^2*3-4*5*(6-7^8*9)$	1190079339	$-1-23*(4+(5^6-7^8)^*9)$
1037664063	$(-1+2)*3-4*5*(6-7^8*9)$	1190079341	$1-23*(4+(5^6-7^8)^*9)$
1037664297	$1^2*3+4*5*(6+7^8*9)$	1190079523	$-1+23*(4-(5^6-7^8)^*9)$
1037664303	$(-1+2)*3+4*5*(6+7^8*9)$	1190079525	$1+23*(4-(5^6-7^8)^*9)$
1037673900	$12*(3^4*5*(6+7^8/9))$	1191876306	$-1-23*(4*5^6-7^8*9)$
1058828751	$(1+2^3(3^4(4+5-6))^*(7+8/9))$	1191876308	$1-23*(4*5^6-7^8*9)$
1078007689	$(-12^3+45)^*(6-7^8/9)$	1192954339	$-1-23*(4+5^6-7^8*9)$
1078027885	$(12^3-45)^*(6+7^8/9)$	1192954341	$1-23*(4+5^6-7^8*9)$
1085880223	$-1+2*((34-5)^6-7^8*9)$	1192954523	$-1+23*(4-5^6+7^8*9)$
1085880225	$1+2*((34-5)^6-7^8*9)$	1192954525	$1+23*(4-5^6+7^8*9)$
1086088791	$(-1+2*3^4/5)^*(6*7^8+9)$	1193172494	$-1-23*(4^5*6-7^8*9)$
1087512559	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5^6-7))^*(8+9)$	1193172496	$1-23*(4^5*6-7^8*9)$
1087512593	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5^6-7))^*(8+9)$	1193290116	$-1-23*(4^5+6-7^8*9)$
1088487407	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5^6+7))^*(8+9)$	1193290118	$1-23*(4^5+6-7^8*9)$
1088487441	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5^6+7))^*(8+9)$	1193290392	$-1-23*(4^5-6-7^8*9)$
1096844814	$-1-23*(4^5(5+6)-7^8*9)$	1193290394	$1-23*(4^5-6-7^8*9)$
1096844816	$1-23*(4^5(5+6)-7^8*9)$	1193307596	$-1-23*(45*6-7^8*9)$
1106375232	$12^3*(-45*6+7^8/9)$	1193307598	$1-23*(45*6-7^8*9)$
1106454720	$12^3*(-4*56+7^8/9)$	1193308654	$-1-23*(4*56-7^8*9)$
1106738112	$12^3*(-4-56+7^8/9)$	1193308656	$1-23*(4*56-7^8*9)$
1106751936	$12^3*(4-56+7^8/9)$	1193312426	$-1-23*(4+56-7^8*9)$
1106753664	$12^3*(-45-6+7^8/9)$	1193312427	$1*23*(-4-56+7^8*9)$
1106774400	$12^3*(-45+6+7^8/9)$	1193312428	$1-23*(4+56-7^8*9)$
1106828832	$12^3*(-45/6+7^8/9)$	1193312610	$-1+23*(4-56+7^8*9)$
1106854752	$12^3*(45/6+7^8/9)$	1193312611	$1*23*(4-56+7^8*9)$
1106909184	$12^3*(45-6+7^8/9)$	1193312612	$1+23*(4-56+7^8*9)$
1106929920	$12^3*(45+6+7^8/9)$	1193312633	$-1-23*(45+6-7^8*9)$
1106931648	$12^3*(-4+56+7^8/9)$	1193312634	$1*23*(-45-6+7^8*9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1193312635	$1-23*(45+6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1297080117	$(-12+(3^{\wedge}4-56)^*7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
1193312794	$-1-23*(4*(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1297080200	$(1+2*3^*4)*(5-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1193312909	$-1-23*(45-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1297080213	$-12+(3^{\wedge}4-56)^*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
1193312910	$1*23*(-45+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1297080237	$12+(3^{\wedge}4-56)^*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
1193312911	$1-23*(45-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1297080250	$(1+2*3^*4)*(-5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1193313484	$-1-23*(4*5-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1297080333	$(12+(3^{\wedge}4-56)^*7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
1193313783	$-1-23*((4-5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1297080500	$(1+2*3^*4)*(5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1193314703	$-1+23*(45-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1297080975	$(1+2*3^*4)*(5*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1193314704	$1*23*(45-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1307544123	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}(4^*5)+6-7)/8-9)$
1193314705	$1+23*(45-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1307544177	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}(4^*5)+6-7)/8+9)$
1193314820	$1+23*(4*(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1308597569	$(-1+2*(3-4^{\wedge}5))*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$
1193314979	$-1+23*(45+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1308622085	$(1-2*(3-4^{\wedge}5))*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
1193314980	$1*23*(45+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1314373233	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*(6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
1193314981	$1+23*(45+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1314373287	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*(6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
1193315002	$-1-23*(4-56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1314375969	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*(6+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
1193315003	$1*23*(-4+56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1314376023	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*(6+7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
1193315004	$1-23*(4-56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1317911094	$(1+2)*((3*(4+5))^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1193315186	$-1+23*(4+56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1323021829	$1/-2-(3/4-5)^*6*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
1193315187	$1*23*(4+56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1323021830	$1/2-(3/4-5)^*6*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
1193315188	$1+23*(4+56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1348961978	$(1-23-4)*(56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1193318958	$-1+23*(4*56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1348964890	$(1-23-4)*(-56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1193318960	$1+23*(4*56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1358809344	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*5)^*6^{\wedge}8(7-8+9)$
1193320016	$-1+23*(45*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1360487892	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6^{\wedge}7-89)$
1193320018	$1+23*(45*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1360490028	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6^{\wedge}7+89)$
1193337220	$-1+23*(4^{\wedge}5-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1362168576	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*5)^*6^{\wedge}8(7-8+9)$
1193337222	$1+23*(4^{\wedge}5-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1373290924	$-1/2-(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}(6+7))/8^*9$
1193337496	$-1+23*(4^{\wedge}5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1373290925	$1/2-(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}(6+7))/8^*9$
1193337498	$1+23*(4^{\wedge}5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1380093519	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)/5)^*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1193455118	$-1+23*(4^{\wedge}5*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1383552213	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5-6)^*7^{\wedge}8-9)$
1193455120	$1+23*(4^{\wedge}5*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1383552267	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5-6)^*7^{\wedge}8+9)$
1193673089	$-1-23*(4-5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1397049741	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
1193673091	$1-23*(4-5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1397049795	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
1193673273	$-1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1400834331	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3*(-456+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1193673275	$1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1400839326	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(-5*6+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
1194751306	$-1+23*(4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1400839380	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(-5*6+7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
1194751308	$1+23*(4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1400843403	$(-1-2)^{\wedge}3*(4*5*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1196548089	$-1-23*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	1400843943	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5+6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
1196548090	$1*23*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	1400843997	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5+6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
1196548091	$1-23*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	1400845130	$-1-(23+4)*(56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1196548273	$-1+23*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	1400845131	$(1*23+4)*(-56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1196548274	$1*23*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	1400845132	$1-(23+4)*(56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1196548275	$1+23*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	1400846373	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5-6+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
1205536949	$-1+23*((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1400846427	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5-6+7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
1205536951	$1+23*((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1400846859	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5-6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
1210608183	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5-6)^*7^{\wedge}8-9)$	1400846913	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5-6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
1210608237	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5-6)^*7^{\wedge}8+9)$	1400848154	$-1+(23+4)*(56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1212653184	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	1400848155	$(1*23+4)*(56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1245191640	$(1+23)*(-4*56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1400848156	$1+(23+4)*(56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1245195576	$(1+23)*(-4-56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1400849289	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5+6+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
1245195768	$(1+23)*(4-56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1400849343	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5+6+7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
1245196080	$(1+23)*(-45+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1400849883	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3*(4*5*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1245197952	$(1+23)*(45-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1400853906	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5*6+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
1245198264	$(1+23)*(-4+56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1400853960	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5*6+7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
1245198456	$(1+23)*(4+56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1400858955	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3*(456+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1245202392	$(1+23)*(4*56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1404643491	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
1253675290	$-1+((2*3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5+67)/89$	1404643545	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
1253675292	$1+((2*3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5+67)/89$	1418141019	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5+6)^*7^{\wedge}8-9)$
1275656679	$(1-(2*3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$	1418141073	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5+6)^*7^{\wedge}8+9)$
1275656697	$(1+(2*3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$	1457346807	$(1-(2*3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)^*9$
1275843303	$(1-(2*3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$	1457346825	$(1+(2*3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)^*9$
1275843321	$(1+(2*3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$	1458653175	$(1-(2*3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8)^*9$
1276327089	$(1+2*(3+4)/5)*(-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1458653193	$(1+(2*3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8)^*9$
1289760759	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$	1470024085	$(1+2/3+4)^*5*(-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1289760777	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$	1470024425	$(1+(2/3+4))^*5*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
1289782798	$-1+23*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1480781249	$-1+2/((3/45)^{\wedge}6/(7*8+9))$
1289782800	$1+23*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1480781251	$1+2/((3/45)^{\wedge}6/(7*8+9))$
1290129399	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$	1487317083	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*(6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
1290129417	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$	1487317137	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*(6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
1293413059	$-1+2*((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1487320179	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*(6+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
1293413061	$1+2*((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1487320233	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*(6+7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
1297079475	$(1+2*3^*4)*(5*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1530081951	$(1+2)*((3+4/5)*(-6-7+8^{\wedge}9))$
1297079950	$(1+2*3^*4)*(-5-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	1530082578	$(1+2)*((3+4/5)*(6*7+8^{\wedge}9))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1531809639	$(1+(2-(3^4-5)*6^7)*8)^*-9$	1733363847	$(-1+(2+(3^4+5)*6^7)*8)^*9$
1531809657	$(1-(2-(3^4-5)*6^7)*8)^*9$	1733363865	$(1+(2+(3^4+5)*6^7)*8)^*9$
1531809927	$(-1+(2+(3^4-5)*6^7)*8)^*9$	1764027202	$1^2*34^*(56+7^8*9)$
1531809945	$(1+(2+(3^4-5)*6^7)*8)^*9$	1764028083	$-1-2-34^*(5^6-7^8*9)$
1555215203	$(1+(2-3^4*5*6)*7^8)/-9$	1764029481	$-1+2+34^*(5+6+7^8*9)$
1557777337	$(1+(2+3^4*5*6)*7^8)/9$	1764029482	$1^2+34^*(5+6+7^8*9)$
1571906249	$-1+2/((3/45)^6/(78-9))$	1764029483	$1+2+34^*(5+6+7^8*9)$
1571906250	$1^2/((3/45)^6/(78-9))$	1764030129	$1+2+34^*(5^6+7^8*9)$
1571906251	$1+2/((3/45)^6/(78-9))$	1764031010	$1^2*34^*(56+7^8*9)$
1579555455	$-1+2^*((3^4+56)*7^8-9)$	1776937490	$-1+2/((3/45)^6/78)-9$
1579555457	$1+2^*((3^4+56)*7^8-9)$	1776937492	$1+2/((3/45)^6/78)-9$
1579555491	$-1+2^*((3^4+56)*7^8+9)$	1776937508	$-1+2/((3/45)^6/78)+9$
1579555493	$1+2^*((3^4+56)*7^8+9)$	1776937510	$1+2/((3/45)^6/78)+9$
1580078125	$(-1+2^*(3^4*5)*6+7-8)^9$	1789970710	$-1+2/(3/4+5)*6^7*8^9$
1583984375	$(1+2^*(3^4*5)*6+7-8)^9$	1789970711	$1+2/(3/4+5)*6^7*8^9$
1584169788	$(-1+234/5)^6*(7^8+9)$	1811738511	$(-1+2/3^4-4^5)^*(6^7*8-9)$
1591085049	$(1+2^*((3^4+5+6)*7^8-9))$	1811753073	$(-1+2/3^4-4^5)^*(6^7*8+9)$
1591085103	$(1+2^*((3^4+5+6)*7^8+9))$	1815910355	$(1-2-34)^*(56-7^8*9)$
1598046875	$(-1+(2^3)^4/5)^*(6+7-8)^9$	1815912077	$(1-2^3)^*(4+5^*(6-7^8*9))$
1601953125	$(1+(2^3)^4/5)^*(6+7-8)^9$	1815912133	$(-1+2^3)^*(4-5^*(6-7^8*9))$
1610231712	$-12^*(3^4*56*7-8^9)$	1815912497	$(1-2^3)^*(4-5^*(6+7^8*9))$
1610287116	$-12^*(3^4*5*67-8^9)$	1815912553	$(-1+2^3)^*(4+5^*(6+7^8*9))$
1610542752	$-12^*(3^4*(5+67)-8^9)$	1815914275	$(1^2+34)^*(56+7^8*9)$
1610543592	$-12^*((3^4+5)*67-8^9)$	1816217469	$(1+2/3^4-4^5)^*(6^7*8-9)$
1610551632	$-12^*((3^4-5)*67-8^9)$	1816232067	$(1+2/3^4-4^5)^*(6^7*8+9)$
1610552472	$12^*(3^4*(5-67)+8^9)$	1823324202	$12^*(3-4/56)^*7^8*9$
1610558220	$-12^*(3^4*56+7-8^9)$	1862993088	$12^3*(-4+5^6*(78-9))$
1610558388	$-12^*(3^4*56-7-8^9)$	1863006912	$12^3*(4+5^6*(78-9))$
1610601228	$-12^*((3^4+56)*7-8^9)$	1867793364	$12^3*(-4-56+7^8*9)$
1610607072	$-12^*(3^4*5+67-8^9)$	1867793507	$-1-(2+34)^*(56-7^8*9)$
1610608680	$-12^*(3^4*5-67-8^9)$	1867793509	$1-(2+34)^*(56-7^8*9)$
1610610636	$-12^*((3^4-56)*7-8^9)$	1867793652	$12^3*(4-56+7^8*9)$
1610614836	$12^*((3^4-56)*7+8^9)$	1867794120	$12^3*(-45+6+7^8*9)$
1610616792	$12^*(3^4*5-67+8^9)$	1867796928	$12^3*(45-6+7^8*9)$
1610618400	$12^*(3^4*5+67+8^9)$	1867797396	$12^3*(-4+56+7^8*9)$
1610624244	$12^*((3^4+56)*7+8^9)$	1867797539	$-1+(2+34)^*(56+7^8*9)$
1610667084	$12^*(3^4*56-7+8^9)$	1867797541	$1+(2+34)^*(56+7^8*9)$
1610667252	$12^*(3^4*56+7+8^9)$	1867797684	$12^3*(4+56+7^8*9)$
1610673000	$-12^*(3^4*(5-67)-8^9)$	1872857880	$12^3*(-4+(5^6+7^8)*9)$
1610673840	$12^*((3^4-5)*67+8^9)$	1872858168	$12^3*(4+(5^6+7^8)*9)$
1610681880	$12^*((3^4+5)*67+8^9)$	1879039119	$-1-2^*(3^4*56-7^8*9)$
1610682720	$12^*(3^4*(5+67)+8^9)$	1879039121	$1-2^*(3^4*56-7^8*9)$
1610938356	$12^*(3^4*5*67+8^9)$	1879057263	$-1+2^*(3^4*56+7^8*9)$
1610993760	$12^*(3^4*56*7+8^9)$	1893486036	$(-12+(3^4-5)*6^7)*89$
1612993838	$(-1+234/(5/6))^*(7^8+9)$	1893487092	$-12+(3^4-5)*6^7*89$
1624523458	$(1+234/(5/6))^*(7^8+9)$	1893487116	$12+(3^4-5)*6^7*89$
1629132951	$(-1+2^*(3^4/5)*6+7^8*9)$	1893488172	$(12+(3^4-5)*6^7)*89$
1632557439	$(1+(2+3^4*(5-6^7))^*8)^*-9$	1908874320	$-1+(2^3*34-5^*(67-8))/9$
1632557457	$(1-(2+3^4*(5-6^7))^*8)^*9$	1908874322	$1+(2^3*34-5^*(67-8))/9$
1632557727	$(-1+(2-3^4*(5-6^7))^*8)^*9$	1908874347	$1+(2^3*34+5-67-8)/9$
1632557745	$(1+(2-3^4*(5-6^7))^*8)^*9$	1912266846	$12^*((3+4/56)*7^8*9)$
1632586335	$-12-3^4*(5-6^7*8^9)$	1917841519	$(1+(2-3^4*5)*6^7)*(-8-9)$
1632586359	$12-3^4*(5-6^7*8^9)$	1917841553	$(1-(2-3^4*5)*6^7)*(8+9)$
1632587145	$-12+3^4*(5+6^7*8^9)$	1919676661	$(-1-2-34)^*(56-7^8*9)$
1632587169	$12+3^4*(5+6^7*8^9)$	1919680805	$(1+2+34)^*(56+7^8*9)$
1632615759	$(1+(2-3^4*(5+6^7))^*8)^*-9$	1923787449	$(-1-2/(3/4/5))^*(6-7-8^9)$
1632615777	$(1-(2-3^4*(5+6^7))^*8)^*9$	1923787621	$(1+2/(3/4/5))^*(6+7+8^9)$
1632616047	$(-1+(2+3^4*(5+6^7))^*8)^*9$	1936877167	$(-1+(2+3^4*5)*6^7)*(8+9)$
1632616065	$(1+(2+3^4*(5+6^7))^*8)^*9$	1936877201	$(1+(2+3^4*5)*6^7)*(8+9)$
1653347508	$(1+234/5)^*(6*(7^8+9))$	1971561906	$12^*(-3+(4-5/6)^*(7^8*9))$
1656876522	$(1+(2-3^4)^5)/(6/-7+8-9)$	1992315456	$12^3/45^*(6+7^8*9)$
1670265054	$(-1+(2-3^4-56)*7^8)/9$	2008294908	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4-5)^*(6-7-8^9)$
1670639523	$(1-2^*(3^4)/(5/(-6-7^8*9)))$	2018021511	$(12+3^4*(5-6^7))^*-89$
1681014213	$(1+2^*(3^4/5*(6-7^8))^*-9)$	2018022567	$-12-3^4*(5-6^7)*89$
1681014231	$(1-2^*(3^4/5*(6-7^8))^*9)$	2018022591	$12-3^4*(5-6^7)*89$
1712145861	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4+(5+6)*7^8*9)$	2018023647	$(12-3^4*(5-6^7))^*89$
1712145933	$(1+2)^*(3^4+(5+6)/7^8-8^9)$	2018058207	$-12-3^4*(5-6^7*89)$
1729440192	$12^*((3^4-56)*7^8-9)$	2018058231	$12-3^4*(5-6^7*89)$
1729440408	$12^*((3^4-56)*7^8+9)$	2018059017	$-12+3^4*(5+6^7*89)$
1732899381	$(1+2^*(3^4/5)*6+7^8*9)$	2018059041	$12+3^4*(5+6^7*89)$
1733363559	$(1+(2-(3^4+5)*6^7)*8)^*-9$	2018093601	$(-12+3^4*(5+6^7))^*89$
1733363577	$(1-(2-(3^4+5)*6^7)*8)^*9$	2018094657	$-12+3^4*(5+6^7)*89$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2018094681	$12+3^4*(5+6^7)*89$		
2018095737	$(12+3^4*(5+6^7))^*89$		
2018236962	$(1+2)*(3^4-4+5)*(-6+7+8^9)$		
2023443423	$-12^3+(45-6)*7^8*9$		
2023446879	$12^3+(45-6)*7^8*9$		
2040675111	$(-1+2/3^4-4*5*(6^7-8))^*9$		
2040675129	$(1+2/3^4-4*5*(6^7-8))^*9$		
2040721767	$(-1+2*3^4*(5/6^7-8))^*9$		
2040721785	$(1+2*3^4*(5/6^7-8))^*9$		
2040733287	$(-1+2*(3^4*5/6^7-8))^*9$		
2040733305	$(1+2*(3^4*5/6^7-8))^*9$		
2040733575	$(-1+2*(3^4*5/6^7+8))^*9$		
2040733593	$(1+2*(3^4*5/6^7+8))^*9$		
2040745095	$(-1+2*3^4*(5/6^7+8))^*9$		
2040745113	$(1+2*3^4*(5/6^7+8))^*9$		
2040791751	$(-1+2/3^4-4*5*(6^7+8))^*9$		
2040791769	$(1+2/3^4-4*5*(6^7+8))^*9$		
2075326120	$(12*3+4)*(-56+7^8*9)$		
2075330600	$(12*3+4)*(56+7^8*9)$		
2101269964	$1/-2+3^4(4+5)/6/7^8-8/9$		
2101269965	$1/2+3^4(4+5)/6/7^8-8/9$		
2105977536	$12^3*(-4+5^6*78-9)$		
2105991360	$12^3*(4+5^6*78-9)$		
2106008640	$12^3*(-4+5^6*78+9)$		
2106022464	$12^3*(4+5^6*78+9)$		
2142629076	$(-12+(3^4+5)*6^7)*89$		
2142630132	$-12+(3^4+5)*6^7*89$		
2142630156	$12+(3^4+5)*6^7*89$		
2142631212	$(12+(3^4+5)*6^7)*89$		

Supplement 2

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
30172	$9 - (8+7*(6-5^4)/3)*21$	96926	$-98+7^6-5^4*(32+1)$
35284	$-9-87*((6-5^4/3)^2-1)$	97779	$-9+87*6*(5^4/3-21)$
35463	$9*(8*(76+5^4/3^2)-1)$	98176	$-98+7^6-5^4*(32-1)$
38101	$-98*(7+6)+5^4*3*21$	98372	$98+7^6-5^4*(32-1)$
38652	$-9+(8-7*6+5^4*3)*21$	99138	$(-9+87)*(6*5^4/3+21)$
40667	$(9-8)*76+5^4*3*21$	99474	$(9+87*6)*(5^4/3-21)$
41786	$(-9-8)*(7*6-5^4*(3+2-1))$	100446	$-9*(87-6*5^4*3)-21$
44825	$9+8*(7^6+5-4^3)/21$	100853	$-9*(8*7-6*(5^4*3+2))-1$
44828	$9+(8*7^6-5+4^3)/21$	100855	$-9*(8*7-6*(5^4*3+2))+1$
47698	$-105*(7-6^5*4/3/21)$	101507	$(9+8)*(76+5^4/3)*21$
48809	$9*8+(7+6)*(5^4*3^2-1)$	101861	$9*(8*7+6*(5^4*3+2))-1$
49072	$9*(8+7*(6/5/4)^{-3}*21)$	102012	$9*(87+6*5^4*3)-21$
52177	$9*-8+7*6*(5^4-3)^2+1$	104480	$-98-(7^6+5/4)*(3^{\wedge}-2-1)$
52808	$98+7*6*((5^4+3)^2-1)$	104609	$9+8*(7+6+(5^4-3)*21)$
52831	$9*8+7*(6*(5^4+3)^2+1)$	105140	$98+7*(6+5^4*(3+21))$
57034	$-9+(8+(7+6)*5^4/3)*21$	105536	$(9+8)*(-7*6+5^4*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
59929	$9+8*7/(6/(5^4*321))$	105572	$-9*8-7^6*(5/(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
60940	$(9-8/7)/(6^{\wedge}5-4*(3+2))^{\wedge}-1$	105716	$9*8-7^6*(5/(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
61549	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)+5^4*(3+2-1)$	106884	$9*(8*7*6*5^4/32+1)$
63332	$(9+8/7)*(-6+5^4*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$	106989	$(9*8+7*6)*(5^4*3/2+1)$
63678	$-9-((8/7-6)/5^{\wedge}-4+3)*21$	109716	$9+8*7*(6+(5^4+3)^2-1)$
63696	$9-((8/7-6)/5^{\wedge}-4+3)*21$	113994	$9*(-8*7*6+(5^4+3)*21)$
64465	$(9+8)*(7*6+5^4*3^2)+1$	115564	$-98*7+6*5^4*(32-1)$
64473	$9-(8-7*6)*(5^4*3+21)$	118700	$9*(8+7*(6+5^4*3+2))-1$
64475	$9*8*(-7*6+5^4*3/2)-1$	118702	$9*(8+7*(6+5^4*3+2))+1$
67312	$9*(-8-7+(6*5^4-3)^2)+1$	118763	$9*(8+7*6*(5^4+3)/2)-1$
67404	$-9-87-6*5^4*(3-21)$	119211	$-9*87+6*(5^4*32-1)$
67418	$9*(-8-7+(6*5^4+3)^2)-1$	119415	$(-9+8*(7+6))*((5^4+3)^2+1)$
67420	$9*(-8-7+(6*5^4+3)^2)+1$	119721	$9+87*6*(5^4/3+21)$
67436	$9*(-8+7+(6*5^4-3)^2)-1$	119980	$-98/7+6*(5^4*32-1)$
67514	$98/7-6*5^4*(3-21)$	120599	$-9+8*(76+5^4*(3+21))$
67562	$9*(8-7+(6*5^4+3)^2)-1$	120617	$9+8*(76+5^4*(3+21))$
67564	$9*(8-7+(6*5^4+3)^2)+1$	120789	$9*87+6*(5^4*32+1)$
67580	$9*(8+7+(6*5^4-3)^2)-1$	121921	$9+8*7/(6/(5^4-3))*21$
67596	$9+87-6*5^4*(3-21)$	125216	$(98-7)*6*(5^4/3+21)$
67814	$-9*(8-7-6*(5^4+3)^2)-1$	126897	$9-(8-76)*(5^4-3)*(2+1)$
68748	$(9+8)*((7+6)*(5^4-3)/2+1)$	127534	$(9+8)*(7+(6*5^4-3)^2+1)$
72509	$9+87/6*5^4*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	127704	$(9+8)*(7+(6*5^4+3)^2-1)$
74696	$(9/8/(7^6*5/(4+3)-2))^{\wedge}-1$	128208	$9*(8+7*6*(5^4/3-21))$
78358	$-98/7+6*(5^4-3)*21$	128937	$9-(8-76)*(5^4*3+21)$
79114	$-98/7+6*(5^4+3)*21$	130302	$9*(-87*6+5^4*(3+21))$
81348	$98+(7+6)*5^4*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	130622	$-98+(7^6-5+4)*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$
84112	$98+7^6*5/(4+3)-21$	130648	$-9*8+(7^6-5+4)*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$
84154	$98+7^6*5/(4+3)+21$	130792	$9*8+(7^6-5+4)*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$
84810	$9*(8+7/6)*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	130818	$98+(7^6-5+4)*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$
86249	$9+8*7/6*5*(43^2-1)$	131993	$9*(8*(7-6+5^4*3)+2)-1$
88068	$9*((8+(7^6-5)/4)/3-21)$	134081	$9*(8*(-7-6+5^4*3)+2)-1$
88114	$-98+(7^6-5)/4*3-21$	134083	$9*(8*(-7-6+5^4*3)+2)+1$
88310	$98+(7^6-5)/4*3-21$	134899	$9*(8*(-7/6+5^4*3)-2)+1$
88352	$98+(7^6-5)/4*3+21$	134933	$9*(8*(-7/6+5^4*3)+2)-1$
89248	$-9+(8-7/6)*(5^4-3)*21$	135053	$9*(8*(7-6+5^4*3)-2)-1$
89477	$-9*(8*(7-6*5^4/3)+2)-1$	135067	$9*(8*(7/6+5^4*3)-2)+1$
89479	$-9*(8*(7-6*5^4/3)+2)+1$	135089	$9*(8*(7-6+5^4*3)+2)-1$
89513	$-9*(8*(7-6*5^4/3)-2)-1$	135101	$9*(8*(7/6+5^4*3)+2)-1$
89685	$-9*(8*(7-6*5^4/3)-21)$	135103	$9*(8*(7/6+5^4*3)+2)+1$
89719	$98*((-7*6+5^4*3)/2-1)$	135917	$9*(8*(7+6+5^4*3)-2)-1$
89897	$9+8*(7+6*5^4*3-21)$	135919	$9*(8*(7+6+5^4*3)-2)+1$
89915	$98*((-7*6+5^4*3)/2+1)$	135923	$(-9+8*7*6)*(5^4/3^2-1)$
90109	$-9+(8-7/6)*(5^4+3)*21$	135953	$9*(8*(7+6+5^4*3)+2)-1$
90127	$9+(8-7/6)*(5^4+3)*21$	135955	$9*(8*(7+6+5^4*3)+2)+1$
90365	$-9+87*6*(5^4/3/2-1)$	136577	$(-9+8*7*6)*(5^4/3^2+1)$
90485	$9*(8*(7+6*5^4/3)-2)-1$	137702	$-9*8-7*((6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
90487	$9*(8*(7+6*5^4/3)-2)+1$	137872	$98-7*((6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
90797	$-98*(7+(6-5^4*3)/2+1)$	138005	$9*(8*(7*6+5^4*3)-2)-1$
91258	$9+87*6*5^4/3/2-1$	138007	$9*(8*(7*6+5^4*3)-2)+1$
91294	$-98-7*(6-(5^4-3)*21)$	138043	$9*(8*(7*6+5^4*3)+2)+1$
91385	$98*(-7+(6+5^4*3)/2-1)$	138372	$98+7^6+5^4*(32+1)$
91490	$98-7*(6-(5^4-3)*21)$	139853	$-98-7*(6-5^4*32+1)$
92117	$-9+87*6*(5^4/3/2+1)$	140352	$-9*(8-76)*(5^4/3+21)$
92135	$9+87*6*(5^4/3/2+1)$	140493	$9*8*(76+5^4*3)+21$
92372	$98-7*(6-(5^4+3)*21)$	141051	$-9*(8-76*(5^4/3-2))+1$
92456	$98+7*(6+(5^4+3)*21)$	141069	$-9*(8-76*(5^4/3-2))-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
141702	$(9*8+7*6)*((5^4-3)^2-1)$	183315	$(9-8/7)*(6^5+4-3)*(2+1)$
141963	$(-9/8+76)*(5^4*3+21)$	183596	$(98-7/6)*(5^4*3+21)$
142086	$-9*(8-76*(5^4/3-2^{\wedge}-1))$	184242	$-9+876*(5^4/3+2)-1$
142239	$-9*(8-76*5^4/3+21)$	184243	$-9+876*(5^4/3+2)/1$
142617	$-9*(8-76*5^4/3-21)$	184244	$-9+876*(5^4/3+2)+1$
142770	$-9*(8-76*(5^4/3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	184261	$9+876*(5^4/3+2)/1$
142817	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}(6-5+4)-3)/2-1)$	184262	$9+876*(5^4/3+2)+1$
142914	$9*(8+76*(5^4/3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	184805	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)/21)$
143070	$(9*8+7*6)*((5^4+3)^2-1)$	184949	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)/21)$
143405	$(9+8*7*6)*(5^4/3*2-1)$	185119	$-9+876*(5^4/3+2+1)$
143787	$-9*(8-76*(5^4/3+2)+1)$	185709	$9*(8*7/6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$
144624	$9*(8+76*(5^4/3+2+1))$	185931	$9*(-8+7*6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$
145475	$9*(-8+(7+6)*(5^4-3)^2)-1$	186146	$(9+876)*(5^4/3+2)+1$
145477	$9*(-8+(7+6)*(5^4-3)^2)+1$	187817	$98*(7*6+5^{\wedge}4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
145558	$(9*87-6)*(5^4/3-21)$	187887	$98*(7*6+5^{\wedge}4*3)+21$
145624	$(-9/(8*(7+6)-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	188020	$(98+7/6)*(5^4*3+21)$
145803	$(9-87)*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)+21$	189089	$9+8*(76*(5^4-3)/2-1)$
146630	$(9+8*7/6)/((5^4)^{\wedge}3-2)^{\wedge}-1$	189958	$(-9-8)*(76+5^{\wedge}4*(3-21))$
147806	$(9*87+6)*(5^4/3-21)$	189989	$9+8*((76*5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1)$
152613	$9+(87-6)*(5^4+3)*(2+1)$	190013	$9+8*((76*5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
152847	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5^4+3+2-1)$	190029	$9+8*((76*5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1)$
156573	$9*(87*6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	190913	$9+8*(76*(5^4+3)/2-1)$
159003	$9*((8+76)*(5^4/3+2)-1)$	195189	$9*(8*(7+6)*5^{\wedge}4/3+21)$
159694	$9*(8-7*6)+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	195992	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4/3-2-1)$
160306	$-9*(8-7*6)+(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	195998	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6*5+43)/(2+1)$
161293	$(9-8+7*6)*(5^4*3*2+1)$	196006	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)/3+21$
163750	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	196018	$-9*8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4/3-2-1)$
163930	$(9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	196160	$98+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)/3-21$
166348	$98+76*5^{\wedge}4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	196162	$9*8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4/3-2-1)$
166685	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	196175	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3)/(2+1)$
167634	$9*(87*(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)-21)$	196188	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4/3-2-1)$
168444	$9+(8+7)*(6*5^{\wedge}4*3-21)$	196194	$98+(7^{\wedge}6*5+43)/(2+1)$
168888	$(-9/(8-76*5^{\wedge}4*32))^{\wedge}-1$	197484	$(98+7)*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)-21$
171192	$(98-7)*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)+21$	198697	$(-9+8*7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3*2-1)$
171673	$(9/(8+(7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	198803	$(-9+8*7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3*2+1)$
174519	$9*(-8*76+5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	198911	$-9*87/(6/(5-43))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
176642	$-9*(8*7+(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	199815	$-9*(8+7)*6+5^{\wedge}4*321$
176644	$-9*(8*7+(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	200484	$-9*(8+7)-6+5^{\wedge}4*321$
176767	$(-9+8*7)*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^2-1)$	200496	$-9*(8+7)+6+5^{\wedge}4*321$
176861	$(-9+8*7)*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^2+1)$	200766	$9*(8+7)+6+5^{\wedge}4*321$
177011	$-9*(8+7+(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	200868	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+5^{\wedge}4*321$
177013	$-9*(8+7+(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	201183	$9*(8*7+6)+5^{\wedge}4*321$
177602	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5/(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	201435	$9*(8+7)*6+5^{\wedge}4*321$
177746	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5/(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	201561	$9*8*(7+6)+5^{\wedge}4*321$
177785	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2)-1$	201995	$-9*(8*7-6*5^{\wedge}4*3*2)-1$
177787	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2)+1$	201997	$-9*(8*7-6*5^{\wedge}4*3*2)+1$
178024	$(-9+876)*(5^4/3-2-1)$	202303	$-9*(8+(7-6/5^{\wedge}-4*3)^2)+1$
178030	$(-9+8*(7+6))*(5^4*3-2+1)$	202697	$9*(8+(7+6/5^{\wedge}-4*3)^2)-1$
178192	$(9*87-6)*(5^4/3+21)$	202699	$9*(8+(7+6/5^{\wedge}-4*3)^2)+1$
178220	$(-9+8*(7+6))*(5^4*3+2-1)$	203003	$9*(8*7+6/5^{\wedge}-4*3*2)-1$
178410	$(-9+8*(7+6))*(5^4*3+2+1)$	203005	$9*(8*7+6/5^{\wedge}-4*3*2)+1$
178890	$(-9+876)*(5^4/3-2)-1$	203448	$9*8*7*((-6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^2-1)$
178891	$(-9+876)*(5^4/3-2)*1$	203891	$(9/(8^{\wedge}7+6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$
178892	$(-9+876)*(5^4/3-2)+1$	203914	$(9/(8+7*(6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)))^{\wedge}-1$
179403	$(9+87)*(-6+5^{\wedge}4*3)-21$	205718	$9-(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4/3)^2+1$
179863	$-9+876*(5^4/3-2-1)$	205785	$9*(8/7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*32)+1)$
179881	$9+876*(5^4/3-2-1)$	205890	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}(6+5-4))/(3+2-1)$
180153	$9*(-8*76+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$	205975	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4/3*21$
180549	$9*(8*7+6+5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	206036	$-9+(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4/3)^2*21$
180555	$(9+87)*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)-21$	206054	$9+(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4/3)^2*21$
180597	$(9+87)*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)+21$	211832	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5-4/(3+2))-1$
180739	$-9+876*(5^4/3-2)/1$	211834	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5-4/(3+2))+1$
180740	$-9+876*(5^4/3-2)+1$	211840	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5-(43+2)^{\wedge}-1)$
180758	$9+876*(5^4/3-2)+1$	213101	$98*(-7-6+5^{\wedge}4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$
182359	$(-9+876)*(5^4/3+2)*1$	213636	$(9*8+7*6)*(5^4*3-2+1)$
182360	$(-9+876)*(5^4/3+2)+1$	213693	$(9*8+7*6)*(5^4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
182408	$98/(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+43)^{\wedge}-2^{\wedge}1$	213864	$(9*8+7*6)*(5^4*3+2-1)$
182605	$(9+876)*(5^4/3-2)*1$	214092	$(9*8+7*6)*(5^4*3+2+1)$
182606	$(9+876)*(5^4/3-2)+1$	215771	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
182929	$-9+876*(5^4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	216552	$9*8*7*((6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^2+1)$
182947	$9+876*(5^4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	218214	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5+43*21)$
183226	$(-9+876)*(5^4/3+2+1)$	219068	$9*(-8+(7+6)*(5^4*3-2))-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
219070	$9^*(-8+(7+6)*(5^4*3-2))+1$	265068	$9^*(8+(7^6-5)/4+32+1)$
219212	$9^*(8+(7+6)*(5^4*3-2))-1$	265092	$9^*(8+(7^6-5)/4)+321$
219214	$9^*(8+(7+6)*(5^4*3-2))+1$	265338	$9^*(8+(7^6-5)/4+3*21)$
219277	$-98+(7+6)*5^4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	268633	$9^*-8^*(7+(6-5^4*3)^2)+1$
220587	$9/8^*((7^6*5-4)/3-2-1)$	269805	$(-9-8^*(7-6/5^{\wedge}-4*3))^*(2+1)$
223346	$(9+8)*(76+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*21)$	269859	$(9-8^*(7-6/5^{\wedge}-4*3))^*(2+1)$
224087	$-9+8^*(7^6*5+4+3)/21$	269917	$9^*8^*(-7/6+5^{\wedge}4*3*2)+1$
224104	$9+(8*(7^6*5+4)+3)/21$	270085	$9^*8^*(7/6+5^{\wedge}4*3*2)+1$
225099	$9+(8+7)^*(6+5^{\wedge}4*(3+21))$	270195	$(9+8^*(7+6/5^{\wedge}-4*3))^*(2+1)$
225702	$-9*(8*(7-6-5^{\wedge}4*321))$	270359	$9^*8^*(-7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^2)-1$
226710	$9^*((87-6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1)$	270361	$9^*8^*(-7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^2)+1$
228897	$9^*((87-6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$	271334	$98/7^*(6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
228915	$9^*((87-6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1)$	271367	$9^*8^*(7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^2)-1$
231942	$9^*(8*7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4/3*2-1)$	271369	$9^*8^*(7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^2)+1$
232711	$-9+8^*((7^6-5)/4-321)$	271371	$(-9+876)*((5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
232729	$9+8^*((7^6-5)/4-321)$	274179	$-9+876^*((5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
232749	$9+8^*((7^6+5)/4-321)$	275485	$-98-7^*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
233058	$9^*(8*7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4/3*2+1)$	275569	$-98+7^*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
234769	$-98+(7^6-5*43)^2-1$	276131	$(9+8)*(((7+6)*5^{\wedge}4-3)^2-1)$
234775	$-9+8^*((7^6-5)/4-3*21)$	276335	$(9+8)*(((7+6)*5^{\wedge}4+3)^2-1)$
234793	$9+8^*((7^6-5)/4-3*21)$	276419	$(9/(8^{\wedge}7-6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)))^{\wedge}-1$
234813	$9+8^*((7^6+5)/4-3*21)$	277005	$(9+876)*((5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
234996	$9+8^*(7^6+5)/4-321$	277559	$(9+8)*((7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^2-1)$
235567	$9^*(8-7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^2)+1$	277593	$(9+8)*((7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^2+1)$
235600	$-9+8^*(7^6-5)/4+321$	278565	$(98+7^*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^*21$
235783	$-9+8^*((7^6-5)/4+3*21)$	280048	$98-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)+21$
236005	$-98-(7-6*5^{\wedge}4*3)^*21$	284244	$-9^*(8-76*(5^{\wedge}4/3*2-1))$
236299	$-98+(7+6*5^{\wedge}4*3)^*21$	284388	$9^*(8+76*(5^{\wedge}4/3*2-1))$
236933	$9^*(-8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^2)-1$	285612	$-9^*(8-76*(5^{\wedge}4/3*2+1))$
237077	$9^*(8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^2)-1$	286161	$(9+8)*(-7*6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
237079	$9^*(8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^2)+1$	287589	$(9+8)*((7*6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)))$
237847	$-9+8^*((7^6-5)/4+321)$	288666	$98/7^*(-6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$
237865	$9+8^*((7^6-5)/4+321)$	290544	$9-(8+7)^*(6-5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
237885	$9+8^*((7^6+5)/4+321)$	290706	$-9+(8+7)^*(6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
237953	$9-8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$	290724	$9+(8+7)^*(6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
240914	$(9^*8+(7^6+5)*43)/21$	292462	$-98+(7^6-5^{\wedge}4)^*(3/2+1)$
242905	$(9^*-8+7)*((6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^2+1)$	292632	$9^*8+(7^6-5^{\wedge}4)^*(3/2+1)$
243035	$(9^*8-7)*((-6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^2+1)$	293468	$(9-8*7)^*(6-5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
244465	$(9^*8-7)*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^2-1)$	294032	$(-9+8*7)^*(6+5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
244595	$(9^*8-7)*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^2+1)$	295613	$-9^*8+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4)^*(3/2+1)$
245497	$(9+8)/(7/(6^{\wedge}5*(4+3^{\wedge}2-1)))$	295757	$9^*8+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4)^*(3/2+1)$
247374	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(4-5+4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$	295783	$98+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4)^*(3/2+1)$
249804	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$	297277	$(9^*8+7)*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^2+1)$
249954	$-9^*8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21$	297311	$(9+(8-76)*5^{\wedge}4/3)^*-21$
250025	$-9+8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21$	302049	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^2-1)$
250069	$9-8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21$	303825	$(9/(8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))))^{\wedge}-1$
250085	$9+8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21$	305451	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^2+1)$
250098	$9^*8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21$	308832	$9/8^*(7^{\wedge}(6+5-4)/3+2+1)$
250140	$9^*8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21$	309294	$9-(8+7)^*(6-5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$
251812	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	312223	$-9+8^*((7^6-5^{\wedge}4)/3+21)$
251943	$9/(8+7)^*((6^{\wedge}5/(4*3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	312241	$9+8^*((7^6-5^{\wedge}4)/3+21)$
251956	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	312825	$9-8^*(7+6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^*21$
252030	$9^*(-8+(7^6*5-4-3)/21)$	313227	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)^*(5+4*321)$
252047	$-9+8*7*(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$	313607	$-9+8^*((7^6+5^{\wedge}4)/3-21)$
253708	$(9+8)*(-76+5^{\wedge}4*(3+21))$	313625	$9+8^*((7^6+5^{\wedge}4)/3-21)$
254941	$9-(8-76)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3*2-1)$	313905	$9+8^*((7^6-5+4)/3+21)$
255077	$9-(8-76)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3*2+1)$	313961	$9+8^*((7^6+5^{\wedge}4)/3+21)$
255795	$(9+876^{\wedge}(-5+4+3))/(2+1)$	313965	$(9+8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^*(-2-1)$
256292	$(9+8)^*(76+5^{\wedge}4*(3+21))$	314019	$(9-8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^*(2+1)$
258029	$9^*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*(4+3)-2)-1$	315205	$9+8^*(7/6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^*21$
260298	$9^*((87+6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1)$	315599	$-9+8^*(76+5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
260316	$9^*((87+6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1)$	317193	$9+8^*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^*21$
261453	$9-8^*(7^6*5+4)/(3-21)$	320392	$(9/(-8*7+(6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$
264141	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(543*2+1)$	326163	$(98+76)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
264306	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5)/4)-321$	327957	$(9+8^*(76+5^{\wedge}4*3))^*21$
264330	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5)/4-32-1)$	328695	$-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)/4*321$
264348	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5)/4-32+1)$	328713	$9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)/4*321$
264411	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5)/4-3-21)$	328849	$-98+(7^6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^*(2+1)$
264450	$9^*(8+(7^6-5)/4)-321$	329045	$98+(7^6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^*(2+1)$
264906	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5)/4+32-1)$	330533	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))/-21$
264948	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5)/4)+321$	331551	$(9+8)*((7^6-5^{\wedge}4)/3/2-1)$
264987	$9^*(8+(7^6-5)/4+3+21)$	331585	$(9+8)*((7^6-5^{\wedge}4)/3/2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
331593	$(9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)/4)*321$	387168	$(9+87)/65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
334012	$(9*8+76*5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	389739	$-9-876+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1$
334509	$(-9-8)*(7+(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	389741	$-9-876+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1$
334747	$(9+8)*(7-(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	389757	$9-876+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1$
336238	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*4*3/21$	389759	$9-876+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1$
339874	$(9/(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3*2)))^{\wedge}-1$	390867	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1$
339991	$-9-(8-76)*5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	390869	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1$
340009	$9-(8-76)*5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	391398	$(-9+87*(6+5^{\wedge}4/3))*21$
342516	$9*876*((5*4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	391493	$-9+876+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1$
345999	$9*(8-7/6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	391511	$9+876+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1$
347224	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*(2+1)$	391578	$-9+87*(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
348666	$9+(87+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3*2-1)$	391596	$9+87*(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
350399	$9*876/(5*4/3)^{\wedge}-2-1$	391776	$(9+87*(6+5^{\wedge}4/3))*21$
350955	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/3-21)$	392082	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4-(3/2)^{\wedge}-1$
350965	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-3)*(2+1)$	392108	$9*-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4-(3/2)^{\wedge}-1$
351179	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3)*(2+1)$	392252	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4-(3/2)^{\wedge}-1$
351301	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3)*(2+1)$	392278	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4-(3/2)^{\wedge}-1$
352085	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4*3)*(2+1)$	396312	$98*((7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1)$
352171	$(-9+8*7)*((6/5^{\wedge}4-4-3)*2-1)$	398076	$98*((7+6)*5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1$
352204	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4*3)*(2+1)$	398898	$9/8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3)*(2+1)$
352400	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4*3)*(2+1)$	399942	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6/5-4+(3+2)^{\wedge}-1)$
353494	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4*3)*(2+1)$	399980	$(98/7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
353500	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*(2+1)$	400020	$(98/7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
353644	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*(2+1)$	400078	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6/5+4+(3+2)^{\wedge}-1)$
353670	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*(2+1)$	400134	$98*((7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1)$
353690	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4*3)*(2+1)$	404272	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)/((6+5)/(4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
354005	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4^{\wedge}3)*(2+1)$	406461	$(9-8*7*6)*((-5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$
354114	$-9*(8+(7-6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21)$	406686	$(-9+(87+6)*5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
354145	$(-9+8*7)*(6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$	407064	$(9+(87+6)*5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
354481	$9*8/(7/6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}-2-1$	407904	$(9+87)*(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
354559	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3)*(2+1)$	409486	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
354575	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3)*(2+1)$	409512	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
354577	$9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3)*(2+1)$	409656	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
354593	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3)*(2+1)$	409682	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
354705	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)/3-21)$	410385	$(-9+8*7*6)*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$
354715	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4-3)*(2+1)$	411039	$(-9+8*7*6)*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$
354929	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3)*(2+1)$	411668	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
354939	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)/3+21)$	411670	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
355212	$9*(87+6+5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$	411696	$9*-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
355374	$9*(-8-7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21)$	411798	$9-(8/(7^{\wedge}6+5)/(4-32))^{\wedge}-1$
356155	$(-9+8*(7+6))*(5^{\wedge}4*3*2-1)$	411847	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
356345	$(-9+8*(7+6))*(5^{\wedge}4*3*2+1)$	411866	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
358288	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/32-1)$	411873	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
358474	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*(2+1)$	411875	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
358484	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/32+1)$	412657	$9*(-87+(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
358670	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*(2+1)$	412675	$9*(-87+(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
362117	$(-9+876)*(5^{\wedge}4/3*2+1)$	412944	$9*(-8*7+(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
364115	$-9+876*(5^{\wedge}4/3*2-1)$	412946	$9*(-8*7+(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
364133	$9+876*(5^{\wedge}4/3*2-1)$	413583	$9*(8+7+(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
365867	$-9+876*(5^{\wedge}4/3*2+1)$	413585	$9*(8+7+(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
365885	$9+876*(5^{\wedge}4/3*2+1)$	413672	$9*8*7*((6*5-4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
367652	$-9/8+7^{\wedge}6*5/4*(3/2+1)$	413861	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
367657	$9*(-87+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	413887	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
367675	$9*(-87+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	413916	$(9+8)*((7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2)-1)$
367944	$9*(-8*7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	413950	$(9+8)*((7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2)+1)$
367946	$9*(-8*7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	413954	$9*(8*7+(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
368315	$9*(-8-7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	414031	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
368583	$9*(8+7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	414057	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
368585	$9*(8+7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	414223	$9*(87+(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
368952	$9*(8*7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	414241	$9*(87+(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
368954	$9*(8*7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	414392	$(9+8)*((7+6)*5^{\wedge}4*3+2-1)$
369223	$9*(87+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	414426	$(9+8)*((7+6)*5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1)$
369635	$(9+876)*(5^{\wedge}4/3*2+1)$	414680	$9*8*7*((6*5-4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
377045	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3)*(2+1)$	414800	$(9+8)*((7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2)-1)$
379491	$(9+8)/(7/((6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3))*2-1))$	416245	$(9+8)/(7/((6*(5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2-1))$
381397	$9+(8+7*(6^{\wedge}5+4)/3)*21$	418324	$(9/8)/((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4-3/2)^{\wedge}-1$
382245	$(-9-8)*((7-6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3)*2+1)$	427614	$(9*8+7*6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3*2+1)$
382449	$(-9-8)/(7/(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3-21))$	428835	$(9+8*7*6)*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$
382755	$(9+8)*((7+6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3)*2+1)$	429525	$(9+8*7*6)*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$
385228	$(9/(8+(7+6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	431470	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4/3*2+1$
386463	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)/21$	432975	$(9+8*7*6)*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$
386659	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)/21$	434469	$-9-87*(6-5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2-1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
434487	$9 \cdot 87^*(6 \cdot 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot (3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$	500106	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 + 3^*2 + 1)$
437054	$9^*8 + 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5/(4+3) + 2 + 1)$	500123	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 + 3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
438677	$9^* (-8 + (7+6)/5^{\wedge} - 4^*3^*2) - 1$	500191	$98 + (7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3^*2 - 1$
438679	$9^* (-8 + (7+6)/5^{\wedge} - 4^*3^*2) + 1$	500193	$98 + (7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3^*2 + 1$
438821	$9^*(8 + (7+6)/5^{\wedge} - 4^*3^*2) - 1$	500446	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 + 3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
438823	$9^*(8 + (7+6)/5^{\wedge} - 4^*3^*2) + 1$	511716	$9 - (8 - (7+6) \cdot 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3) \cdot 21$
444117	$9 - (8 - 7^*6) \cdot (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) \cdot 21$	520910	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)/2) - 1$
444452	$(9/(8^*7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5/4+3) + 2))^{\wedge} - 1$	520912	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)/2) + 1$
444805	$(9+8) \cdot (7^* (-6 + 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3) \cdot 2 - 1)$	521054	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)/2) - 1$
447661	$(9+8) \cdot (7^* (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3) \cdot 2 - 1)$	521056	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)/2) + 1$
447695	$(9+8) \cdot (7^* (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3) \cdot 2 + 1)$	522790	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5 + 4) \cdot (3^{\wedge} - 2 - 1)$
450935	$9^* \cdot 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot (4 - (3^*2)^{\wedge} - 1)$	522816	$9^* \cdot 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5 + 4) \cdot (3^{\wedge} - 2 - 1)$
451079	$9^*8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot (4 - (3^*2)^{\wedge} - 1)$	522986	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5 + 4) \cdot (3^{\wedge} - 2 - 1)$
451105	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot (4 - (3^*2)^{\wedge} - 1)$	524637	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) \cdot (5^*432 - 1)$
455800	$9^*8 + 7/6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4 \cdot (3/2) - 1)$	525123	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6) \cdot (5^*432 + 1)$
457232	$((9+8)/(7 - 65^*43)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge} - 1$	526914	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 543)/2 + 1)$
463980	$9^*(8 + 7/6) \cdot (5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	527634	$(98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4) \cdot (3 - 21)$
464991	$-9 + (87+6) \cdot 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	528233	$(-9 + 8^*7) \cdot (6^* (5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3 - 2) + 1)$
467998	$-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot (3 + 2 - 1)$	528372	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*43)/2 - 1)$
468168	$9^*8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot (3 + 2 - 1)$	528410	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4/3)/2) - 1$
468423	$-9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 543)/2 + 1)$	528412	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4/3)/2) + 1$
468425	$9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 543)/2 - 1)$	528534	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*43)/2 + 1)$
468441	$9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 543)/2 + 1)$	528554	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4/3)/2) - 1$
469753	$9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*43)/2 + 1)$	528556	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4/3)/2) + 1$
469947	$-9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 54^*3)/2 + 1)$	528609	$(9^*(8+7)+6) \cdot (5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^*2 - 1)$
469949	$9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 54^*3)/2 - 1)$	528797	$(-9 + 8^*7) \cdot (6^* (5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3 + 2 - 1))$
469965	$9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 54^*3)/2 + 1)$	529037	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4^{\wedge}3)/2) - 1$
470405	$9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 43)/2 - 1)$	529082	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}3)/2) - 1$
470409	$9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 54 + 3)/2 + 1)$	529084	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}3)/2) + 1$
470462	$-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) \cdot (3 + 2 - 1)$	529101	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 54 - 3)/2 + 1)$
470730	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) \cdot (3 + 2 - 1)$	529183	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4^{\wedge}3)/2) + 1$
470774	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4) \cdot (3 + 2 - 1)$	529267	$(-9 + 8^*7) \cdot (6^* (5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3 + 2) - 1)$
470787	$-9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 43)/2 + 1)$	529319	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4/3)/2) - 1$
471227	$-9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 54^*3)/2 - 1)$	529333	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4/3)/2) + 1$
471243	$-9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 54^*3)/2 + 1)$	529508	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4/3)/2) - 1$
471245	$9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 54^*3)/2 - 1)$	529522	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4/3)/2) + 1$
471261	$9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 54^*3)/2 + 1)$	529523	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4^*3)/2) - 1$
471439	$-9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*43)/2 - 1)$	529525	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4^*3)/2) + 1$
471473	$9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*43)/2 + 1)$	529570	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4 - 3)/2) + 1$
472051	$-9^*(8 - 7^*(6/5^{\wedge} - 4 - 3) \cdot 2) + 1$	529658	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge}3)/2) - 1$
472193	$9^*(8 + 7^*(6/5^{\wedge} - 4 - 3) \cdot 2) - 1$	529660	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge}3)/2) + 1$
472195	$-9^*(8 + 7^*(6/5^{\wedge} - 4 - 3) \cdot 2) + 1$	529757	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge}3)/2) - 1$
472481	$9^* (-8 + (7^*6/5^{\wedge} - 4 + 3) \cdot 2) - 1$	529759	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge}3)/2) + 1$
472625	$9^*(8 + (7^*6/5^{\wedge} - 4 + 3) \cdot 2) - 1$	529802	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge}3)/2) - 1$
472627	$9^*(8 + (7^*6/5^{\wedge} - 4 + 3) \cdot 2) + 1$	529804	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge}3)/2) + 1$
472751	$-9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 543)/2 - 1)$	530285	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4/3)/2) - 1$
472769	$9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 543)/2 - 1)$	530287	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4/3)/2) + 1$
472785	$9 + 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 543)/2 + 1)$	530307	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*43)/2 - 1)$
472805	$-9^*(8 - 7^*(6/5^{\wedge} - 4 + 3) \cdot 2) - 1$	530429	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4/3)/2) - 1$
472807	$-9^*(8 - 7^*(6/5^{\wedge} - 4 + 3) \cdot 2) + 1$	530451	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*43)/2 - 1)$
472949	$9^*(8 + 7^*(6/5^{\wedge} - 4 + 3) \cdot 2) - 1$	531783	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 543)/2 - 1)$
472951	$9^*(8 + 7^*(6/5^{\wedge} - 4 + 3) \cdot 2) + 1$	534280	$(-9 + 8^*(7+6)) \cdot (5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
473024	$-9^*8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot (3 + 2 - 1)$	534470	$(-9 + 8^*(7+6)) \cdot (5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
473168	$9^*8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot (3 + 2 - 1)$	536903	$9^*8^* (-7 + 6^*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3) \cdot 2) - 1$
473194	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot (3 + 2 - 1)$	536905	$9^*8^* (-7 + 6^*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3) \cdot 2) + 1$
474695	$9^* (-8 + 7^*6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) \cdot 2) - 1$	537785	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)/2) - 1$
474697	$9^* (-8 + 7^*6 \cdot (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) \cdot 2) + 1$	537913	$9^*8^*(7 + 6^*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3) \cdot 2) + 1$
474839	$9^*(8 + 7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4 + 3) \cdot 2) - 1$	537931	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)/2) + 1$
474841	$9^*(8 + 7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4 + 3) \cdot 2) + 1$	542087	$9^*8^* (-7 + 6^*(5^{\wedge}4 + 3) \cdot 2) - 1$
483621	$(9^*(8+7) - 6) \cdot (5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^*2 - 1)$	542089	$9^*8^* (-7 + 6^*(5^{\wedge}4 + 3) \cdot 2) + 1$
485095	$(9^*8 - 7) \cdot (6^*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3) \cdot 2 - 1)$	542491	$-9 + ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)/21$
485225	$(9^*8 - 7) \cdot (6^*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3) \cdot 2 + 1)$	542509	$9 + ((8+7)^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)/21$
490950	$9 + 87^*(6 + 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3) \cdot (2 + 1)$	543095	$9^*8^*(7 + 6^*(5^{\wedge}4 + 3) \cdot 2) - 1$
493551	$9^*87^*(6 + 5^{\wedge}4 - (3/2)^{\wedge} - 1)$	543097	$9^*8^*(7 + 6^*(5^{\wedge}4 + 3) \cdot 2) + 1$
494530	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 - 321)$	543219	$-9 - 87^*(6 - 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot (3^{\wedge}2 + 1))$
494595	$9^*87^*(6 + 5^{\wedge}4 + (3/2)^{\wedge} - 1)$	543237	$9 - 87^*(6 - 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot (3^{\wedge}2 + 1))$
499121	$98 + (7/(6 - 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge} - 1$	548702	$98 + 7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3) \cdot 21$
499528	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 - 3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	548980	$9^* \cdot 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot (4 + (3/2)^{\wedge} - 1)$
499624	$(-9 - 8/76)/(5 - 43)^{\wedge}(-2 - 1)$	548996	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4^*3)/21$
499817	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 - 3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	549038	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4 + 3)/21$
499868	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 - 3^*2 - 1)$	549124	$9^*8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot (4 + (3/2)^{\wedge} - 1)$
499953	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4 - 3 + 2 - 1)$	549150	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot (4 + (3/2)^{\wedge} - 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
550172	$98*(7-(6-5^4*3)*(2+1))$	661803	$9/8*(7^6*5+43)-21$
551789	$98+7*(6*5^4+3)*21$	661845	$9/8*(7^6*5+43)+21$
552328	$98*(-7+(6+5^4*3)*(2+1))$	663085	$(9+8)*((7^6-5^4)/3-2-1)$
553700	$98*(7+(6+5^4*3)*(2+1))$	663187	$(9+8)*((7^6-5^4)/3+2+1)$
553798	$-98+7*6*(5^4+3)*21$	663799	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4*321)$
553994	$98+7*6*(5^4+3)*21$	663817	$9-8*(7^6-5^4*321)$
558842	$9-(8/(7^6*(5-43)-2))^{-1}$	666621	$(9+8)*((7^6-5+4)/3-2-1)$
563928	$9*(-8+(7*6+5^4/3)^2)-1$	666740	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4)/3-2-1)$
563930	$9*(-8+(7*6+5^4/3)^2)+1$	666842	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4)/3+2+1)$
564072	$9*(8+(7*6+5^4/3)^2)-1$	670072	$(9+8)*7*(6+5^4*3^2)-1$
564074	$9*(8+(7*6+5^4/3)^2)+1$	670106	$(9+8)*7*(6+5^4*3^2)+1$
564237	$(9/(8+(7+6)*5^4*(3/2)))^{-1}$	670667	$(9+8)*76+5^4*3*21$
569383	$-9+8*76*(5^4*3/2-1)$	672103	$-9+8*(7^6*5/(4+3))-21$
569401	$9+8*76*(5^4*3/2-1)$	672121	$9+8*(7^6*5/(4+3))-21$
570617	$9+8*76*(5^4*3/2+1)$	672457	$9+8*(7^6*5/(4+3)+21)$
570843	$(9+8)*(7+6/5)*4^{(3*2)-1}$	679975	$9-(8-7^6)*(5^4*32-1)$
576312	$9*8-7^6*5*((4+3)^{-2}-1)$	680043	$9-(8-7^6)*(5^4*32+1)$
581241	$-9+(87+6)*5^4*(3^2+1)$	681505	$-9*8+(7+6)/(5/(4^3*2+1))$
589577	$(9*8+7)*(6*(5^4-3)*2-1)$	681675	$98+(7+6)/5*(4^3*2+1)$
592524	$9+(8+7)*(6+5^4*3)*21$	702428	$(-9+(8*7)^{-6+5+4})*3(2+1)$
595265	$(9*8+7)*(6*(5^4+3)*2-1)$	702500	$(9+(8*7)^{-6+5+4})*3(2+1)$
595423	$(9*8+7)*(6*(5^4+3)*2+1)$	703512	$(-98+(7^6-5)/4)*3(2+1)$
599088	$-9+(8^7*6-5^4*3)/21$	704394	$9*(-8+7^6-5^4*3*21)$
599106	$9+(8^7*6-5^4*3)/21$	704538	$9*(8+7^6-5^4*3*21)$
600178	$-9*8+7^6*5*((4+3)^{-2}+1)$	704565	$-9*(87-6*(5^4-3)*21)$
600322	$9*8+7^6*5*((4+3)^{-2}+1)$	705213	$-9*(8+7-6*(5^4-3)*21)$
606717	$-9*(87+6*5^4*(3-21))$	705435	$9*((-8+(7^6-54)/3)^2+1)$
612402	$98*(-7+6+5^4*(3^2+1))$	705489	$9*(-8+(7^6-54)/3^2-1)$
613774	$98*(7+6+5^4*(3^2+1))$	705507	$9*(-8+(7^6-54)/3^2+1)$
615538	$9/87*(65^4/3+2)-1$	706107	$-9+(8+(7^6+5)/4)*3(2+1)$
615539	$9/87*(65^4/3+2)/1$	706133	$9*(8+7^6/5)*(4/3+2)-1$
615540	$9/87*(65^4/3+2)+1$	706135	$9*((8+7^6/5)*(4/3+2))+1$
616616	$98*(7*6+5^4*(3^2+1))$	706137	$9*(-8+(7^6+54)/3^2-1)$
617470	$-98+((7^6-5)/4-3)*21$	706155	$9*(-8+(7^6+54)/3^2+1)$
617596	$-98+((7^6-5)/4+3)*21$	706353	$9*((8+(7^6+54)/3)^2-1)$
617666	$98+((7^6-5)/4-3)*21$	706371	$9*((8+(7^6+54)/3)^2+1)$
617792	$98+((7^6-5)/4+3)*21$	707400	$9*(-87+(6*5^4-3)*21)$
617853	$-9+(8+(7^6-5)/4+3)*21$	707921	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4*3-2))-1$
617871	$9+(8+(7^6-5)/4+3)*21$	707923	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4*3-2))+1$
626183	$-9+8*(7^6-5^4*3*21)$	708065	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4*3-2))-1$
626201	$9+8*(7^6-5^4*3*21)$	708067	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4*3-2))+1$
626929	$9-8*(7-6*(5^4-3)*21)$	708216	$(98+(7^6-5)/4)*3(2+1)$
627041	$9+8*(7+6*(5^4-3)*21)$	708276	$(98+(7^6+5)/4)*3(2+1)$
628833	$9+8*7*(6/5^4-4^3-21)$	709433	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4*3+2))-1$
630457	$9-8*(7-(6*5^4+3)*21)$	711359	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4(4+3))^2)-1$
630569	$9+8*(7+(6*5^4+3)*21)$	711361	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4(4+3))^2)+1$
632399	$9+(8/((7^6+5)*43-2))^{-1}$	711503	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4(4+3))^2)-1$
632977	$9-8*(7-6*(5^4+3)*21)$	711505	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4(4+3))^2)+1$
633089	$9+8*(7+6*(5^4+3)*21)$	712017	$-9*(8+7-6*(5^4+3)*21)$
639107	$98*(7*(-6+5^4*3/2)+1)$	712935	$9*(87+6*(5^4+3)*21)$
640494	$-9*(8-76*(5^4*3/2-1))$	723807	$-9/(8/7-6)*(5^4*(3/2)+1)$
640638	$9*(8+76*(5^4*3/2-1))$	730405	$(9*8-7)*(6*(5^4*3-2)-1)$
640969	$98*(7*(-6+5^4*3)/2-1)$	730535	$(9*8-7)*(6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$
641165	$98*(7*(-6+5^4*3)/2+1)$	730688	$-98*(7-6*(5^4-3)*21)$
641862	$-9*(8-76*(5^4*3/2+1))$	731145	$9-8*7*(6-(5^4-3)*21)$
645281	$98*(7*(6+5^4*3)/2+1)$	731374	$-98*(7-6*((5^4-3)^2+1))$
645840	$(9+8*7*6)*(5^4*3-2-1)$	731965	$(9*8-7)*(6*(5^4*3+2)-1)$
646530	$(9+8*7*6)*(5^4*3-2+1)$	737744	$-98*(7-6*(5^4+3)*21)$
647143	$98*(7*(6+5^4*3/2)-1)$	737940	$-98*(7-6*(5^4+3)*2-1)$
647339	$98*(7*(6+5^4*3/2)+1)$	738201	$9-8*7*(6-(5^4+3)*21)$
648855	$9+8*7*6*((5^4-3)*2-1)$	738430	$-98*(7-6*((5^4+3)*2+1))$
649290	$9+8*7*6*((5^4-3)*2-1)$	738873	$9+8*7*(6+(5^4+3)*21)$
649464	$9+8*7*(6*(5^4-3)*2+1)$	750126	$9-(8-(7/(6/54)))^3*(2+1)$
649899	$9+8*7*6*((5^4-3)*2+1)$	750174	$9+(8+(7/(6/54)))^3*(2+1)$
652944	$9+8*7*((6*5^4+3)*2-1)$	756054	$9*(-8+7^6*5/(4+3))-21$
653682	$9*8+(7^6*5+4)*(3^2-2+1)$	756353	$9+8*(76*(5^4-3)*2-1)$
655119	$9+8*7*6*((5^4+3)*2-1)$	756432	$9*(-8+7^6*5/(4+3)+21)$
655554	$9+8*7*(6*(5^4+3)*2-1)$	759132	$9^4((8+7)/6)*5^4*(3+2)-1$
655571	$98+7^6*(5+4*3/21)$	759618	$9^4((8+7)/6)*5^4*(3+2)+1$
655728	$9+8*7*(6*(5^4+3)*2+1)$	763649	$9+8*(76*(5^4+3)*2-1)$
659409	$9+(8*7-6)*(5^4+3)*21$	764614	$9*-8+(7^6-5)*(4+3/2+1)$
661410	$9/8*(7^6*5-4-321)$	764679	$9*-8+(7^6+5)*(4+3/2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
764758	$9*8+(7^6-5)*(4+3/2+1)$	824278	$(9+8+(7^6+54)/3)*21$
764784	$98+(7^6-5)*(4+3/2+1)$	824677	$(9*8+(7^6-54)/3)*21$
764823	$9*8+(7^6+5)*(4+3/2+1)$	825461	$(98+(7^6-5*4)/3)*21$
764849	$98+(7^6+5)*(4+3/2+1)$	825538	$(98+(7^6-5-4)/3)*21$
776183	$-9+8*(7^6-5^4*(32+1))$	825608	$(98+(7^6+5-4)/3)*21$
776201	$9+8*(7^6-5^4*(32+1))$	825664	$(98+(7^6+5+4)/3)*21$
781175	$-9+8*(7^6-5^4*32-1)$	825741	$(98+(7^6+5*4)/3)*21$
786183	$-9+8*(7^6-5^4*(32-1))$	825860	$(-98+(7^6+5^4)/3)*21$
786201	$9+8*(7^6-5^4*(32-1))$	826884	$9+(8+7+6)*5^4*3*21$
793836	$9*(8+(7^6-5)/4*3-21)$	827741	$-9-(8-(7^6+5^4)/3)*21$
793862	$9*((-8+(7^6-5)/4)*3-2)-1$	827759	$9-(8-(7^6+5^4)/3)*21$
793864	$9*((-8+(7^6-5)/4)*3-2)+1$	828077	$-9+(8+(7^6+5^4)/3)*21$
793900	$9*((-8+(7^6-5)/4)*3+2)+1$	828095	$9+(8+(7^6+5^4)/3)*21$
793999	$-98+(7^6-5)/4*3^2(2+1)$	828529	$(9+8)*(7+6)*5^4*3*2-1$
794092	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)/4*3)-2^{\wedge}1-1$	828733	$(9+8)*((7+6)*5^4*3*2-1)$
794093	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)/4*3)+2^{\wedge}1-1$	828767	$(9+8)*((7+6)*5^4*3*2+1)$
794139	$9+(8/(7^6*54-3^2))^{\wedge}1$	828971	$(9+8)*(7+6)*(5^4*3*2+1)$
794143	$(98*7^6*54)/(3^2-1)$	829134	$9*876*(5^4/3/2+1)$
794195	$98+(7^6-5)/4*3^2(2+1)$	829976	$(98+(7^6+5^4)/3)*21$
794236	$9*(8+(7^6+5)/4*3)-2^{\wedge}1-1$	831150	$-9*(8-7*(6+(5^4+3)*21))$
794237	$9*(8+(7^6+5)/4*3)+2^{\wedge}1-1$	835679	$-9+8*(7^6-(5^4+3)*21)$
794502	$9*((8+(7^6-5)/4)*3+21)$	835697	$9+8*(7^6-(5^4+3)*21)$
809477	$-9*(8*(7-6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3)+2)-1$	836687	$-9+8*(7^6-(5^4-3)*21)$
809479	$-9*(8*(7-6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3)+2)+1$	836705	$9+8*(7^6-(5^4-3)*21)$
809513	$-9*(8*(7-6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3)-2)-1$	839860	$-9+7*6*(5^4*32-1)$
809515	$-9*(8*(7-6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3)-2)+1$	840091	$98+7*(6*5^4*32-1)$
809853	$9+(8*7+6)*(5^4-3)*21$	840140	$98+7*6*(5^4*32+1)$
810470	$(9/(-8+7^6*(5^4*3+2)))^{\wedge}1-1$	850140	$-9*(8-76*((5^4-3)*2-1))$
810485	$9*(8*(7+6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3)-2)-1$	851183	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4*(3-21))$
810487	$9*(8*(7+6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3)-2)+1$	851201	$9+8*(7^6+5^4*(3-21))$
810521	$9*(8*(7+6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3)+2)-1$	856226	$98*(7*(6*5^4/3-2)+1)$
810523	$9*(8*(7+6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3)+2)+1$	857085	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4-3)/21)$
813366	$9*876*(5^4/3/2-1)$	857229	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4-3)/21)$
817665	$9*(8*7+6)*(5^4+3)*21$	858348	$-9*(8-76*((5^4+3)*2-1))$
818991	$-9-(8-(7^6-5^4)/3)*21$	859716	$-9*(8-76*((5^4+3)*2+1))$
819009	$9-(8-(7^6-5^4)/3)*21$	871906	$98*7*(6*5^4/3+21)$
820461	$-9*(8-7/(6/(5^4(4+3)+21)))$	873144	$9*(8+7^6-5^4*(32+1))$
821201	$9+8*(7^6-5^4*(3+21))$	874557	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5^4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
821226	$(98+(7^6-5^4)/3)*21$	875043	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5^4*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
821345	$(-98+(7^6-5^4)/3)*21$	875862	$(-9+87)*(6*5^4*3-21)$
821422	$(-98+(7^6-5-4)/3)*21$	878778	$9*(-8+7^6-5^4*32+1)$
821478	$(-98+(7^6-5+4)/3)*21$	878922	$9*(8+7^6-5^4*32+1)$
821492	$(-98+(7^6+5-4)/3)*21$	880092	$9*87*6*(5^4/3-21)$
821548	$(-98+(7^6+5+4)/3)*21$	880910	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3))/2)-1$
821653	$(-9*8+(7^6-54)/3)*21$	880912	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3))/2)+1$
822117	$-9+876*(5^4*3/2+1)$	881054	$9*(8+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3))/2)-1$
822135	$9+876*(5^4*3/2+1)$	881056	$9*(8+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3))/2)+1$
822409	$(-9*8+(7^6+54)/3)*21$	882232	$-98+(7^6-5)*(4+3+2^{\wedge}1-1)$
822456	$-9*(8+7*(6-(5^4-3)*21))$	882258	$-9*8+(7^6-5)*(4+3+2^{\wedge}1-1)$
822808	$(-9-8+(7^6-54)/3)*21$	882333	$9*-8+(7^6+5)*(4+3+2^{\wedge}1-1)$
822988	$-9-(8-(7^6-54)/3)*21$	882402	$9*8+(7^6-5)*(4+3+2^{\wedge}1-1)$
823144	$(-9+8+(7^6-54)/3)*21$	882477	$9*8+(7^6+5)*(4+3+2^{\wedge}1-1)$
823244	$9-(8-(7^6-5^4)/3)*21$	882503	$98+(7^6+5)*(4+3+2^{\wedge}1-1)$
823303	$-9-(8-(7^6-5-4)/3)*21$	884394	$9*(-8+7^6-5^4*(32-1))$
823321	$9-(8-(7^6-5-4)/3)*21$	884538	$9*(8+7^6-5^4*(32-1))$
823324	$-9+(8+(7^6-54)/3)*21$	887723	$(9*8+7)*(6*(5^4*3-2)-1)$
823342	$9+(8+(7^6-54)/3)*21$	887881	$(9*8+7)*(6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$
823377	$9-(8-(7^6-5+4)/3)*21$	888199	$(9+8)*(7*6*(5^4-3)*2-1)$
823657	$9+(8+(7^6-5-4)/3)*21$	888233	$(9+8)*(7*6*(5^4-3)*2+1)$
823709	$-9+(8+(7^6+5-4)/3)*21$	888335	$(9+8)*7*(6*(5^4-3)*2+1)$
823713	$9+(8+(7^6-5+4)/3)*21$	889619	$(9*8+7)*(6*(5^4*3+2)-1)$
823727	$9+(8+(7^6+5-4)/3)*21$	891769	$(9+8)*(7*(6/5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$
823744	$-9-(8-(7^6+54)/3)*21$	891803	$(9+8)*(7*(6/5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$
823762	$9-(8-(7^6+54)/3)*21$	892428	$-9-((8-76)*5^4+3)*21$
823765	$-9+(8+(7^6+5+4)/3)*21$	892446	$9-((8-76)*5^4+3)*21$
823783	$9+(8+(7^6+5+4)/3)*21$	892572	$9-((8-76)*5^4-3)*21$
823822	$9*(8+7^6/5)*(4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$	892585	$(9+8)*((7*6/5^{\wedge}4-4+3)*2-1)$
823824	$9*(8+7^6/5)*(4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$	892619	$(9+8)*((7*6/5^{\wedge}4-4+3)*2+1)$
823842	$-9+(8+(7^6+5^4)/3)*21$	893197	$(9+8)*(7*(6/5^{\wedge}4-4+3)*2-1)$
823860	$9+(8+(7^6+5^4)/3)*21$	893231	$(9+8)*(7*(6/5^{\wedge}4-4+3)*2+1)$
823942	$(9-8+(7^6+54)/3)*21$	894740	$(98-7/6)*5*(43^{\wedge}2-1)$
824098	$9+(8+(7^6+54)/3)*21$	896665	$(9+8)*7*(6*(5^4+3)*2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
896767	$(9+8)*(7*6*(5^4+3)*2-1)$	998009	$9+(876-5^4*3)^2-1$
896801	$(9+8)*(7*6*(5^4+3)*2+1)$	998011	$9+(876-5^4*3)^2+1$
896903	$(9+8)*7*(6*(5^4+3)*2+1)$	999413	$(9+8)*((7^6-5-4^3)/2-1)$
901975	$(9/(-8+7^6*(5+4^3)+2))^{\wedge-1}$	999447	$(9+8)*((7^6-5-4^3)/2+1)$
906867	$9*((87-6)*(5^4-3)*2-1)$	999498	$(9+8)*((7^6+5-4^3)/2-1)$
906885	$9*((87-6)*(5^4-3)*2+1)$	999736	$(9+8)*((7^6-5*(4+3))/2+1)$
908703	$(-98+(7^6-5)/4)*(32-1)$	999804	$(9+8)*((7^6-5*4-3)/2-1)$
911643	$-98+(7^6-5)/4*(32-1)$	999889	$(9+8)*((7^6-5-4^3)/2+1)$
911839	$98+(7^6-5)/4*(32-1)$	1000195	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4+3)/2-1)$
911980	$-9+(8+(7^6-5)/4)*(32-1)$	1000229	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4+3)/2+1)$
914779	$(98+(7^6-5)/4)*(32-1)$	1000263	$(9+8)*((7^6+(5+4)^3)/2+1)$
915615	$9*((87-6)*(5^4+3)*2-1)$	1000535	$(9+8)*((7^6-5+4^3)/2+1)$
915633	$9*((87-6)*(5^4+3)*2+1)$	1000586	$(9+8)*((7^6+5+4^3)/2-1)$
916300	$(98+7/6)*5*(43^2-1)$	1004454	$9*8/7*(6/5^4/3)^{\wedge-2-1}$
923769	$9*(-8+7^6-5^4*(3+21))$	1004615	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4)/2-1)$
926033	$9+8*(7^6-5^4*3-21)$	1004649	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4)/2+1)$
928119	$(9/(-8+7^6*(5+4^3+2)))^{\wedge-1}$	1015937	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4*3)/2-1)$
936094	$-98+(7^6-5^4)*(3^2-1)$	1015971	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4*3)/2+1)$
936290	$98+(7^6-5^4)*(3^2-1)$	1021839	$(98-7)^*(6*5^4*3-21)$
940077	$9*(-8+7^6-(5^4+3)*21)$	1024923	$9^8/(7^6)+5/(4+(3/2)^{\wedge-1})$
940221	$9*(8+7^6-(5^4+3)*21)$	1025018	$9*(-8+7^6-5^4*3^2)-1$
941957	$9*(8*7*(-6+5^4*3)-2)-1$	1025020	$9*(-8+7^6-5^4*3^2)+1$
941995	$9*(8*7*(-6+5^4*3)+2)+1$	1025088	$9*8*76*(5^4/3-21)$
944064	$9*8*(-76+(5^4+3)*21)$	1025162	$9*(8+7^6-5^4*3^2)-1$
945936	$9*8*(76+(5^4-3)*21)$	1025164	$9*(8+7^6-5^4*3^2)+1$
946094	$-98+(7^6+5^4)*(3^2-1)$	1031183	$-9+8*(7^6-5^4*(3-21))$
946290	$98+(7^6+5^4)*(3^2-1)$	1031201	$9+8*(7^6-5^4*(3-21))$
947879	$9*8*(7*(6+5^4*3)-2)-1$	1035216	$(98-7)*6*(5^4*3+21)$
947881	$9*8*(7*(6+5^4*3)-2)+1$	1040393	$9+8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*(4-32^{\wedge-1})$
948005	$9*(8*7*(6+5^4*3)-2)-1$	1041219	$9*((87+6)*(5^4-3)*2-1)$
948007	$9*(8*7*(6+5^4*3)-2)+1$	1041237	$9*((87+6)*(5^4-3)*2+1)$
948041	$9*(8*7*(6+5^4*3)+2)-1$	1041705	$9*(-8+7^6-5^4*3-21)$
948043	$9*(8*7*(6+5^4*3)+2)+1$	1041849	$9*(8+7^6-5^4*3-21)$
948167	$9*8*(7*(6+5^4*3)+2)-1$	1045133	$9*(8*7+6)*(5^4*3-2)-1$
948169	$9*8*(7*(6+5^4*3)+2)+1$	1045135	$9*(8*7+6)*(5^4*3-2)+1$
956351	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4*3+21)$	1045467	$-9*(87-6*5^4*(32-1))$
957519	$9*(-8+7^6+5^4*(3-21))$	1045679	$-9+8*(7^6+(5^4-3)*21)$
959905	$9-8*(7-6*(5^4*32-1))$	1045697	$9+8*(7^6+(5^4-3)*21)$
959945	$9-8*(7-6*5^4*32+1)$	1046687	$-9+8*(7^6+(5^4+3)*21)$
960017	$9+8*(7+6*(5^4*32-1))$	1047365	$9*(8*7+6)*(5^4*3+2)-1$
960057	$9+8*(7+6*5^4*32-1)$	1047367	$9*(8*7+6)*(5^4*3+2)+1$
960113	$9+8*(7+6*(5^4*32+1))$	1047464	$9*(-8+7^6-(5^4+3)*2)-1$
960890	$98*((7^6+5)/4/3+2^{\wedge-1})$	1047466	$9*(-8+7^6-(5^4+3)*2)+1$
962899	$98*((7^6+5)/4/3+21)$	1047572	$9*(-8+7^6-(5^4-3)*2)-1$
967329	$(-98+(7^6-5)/4)*(32+1)$	1047574	$9*(-8+7^6-(5^4-3)*2)+1$
970465	$-98+(7^6-5)/4*(32+1)$	1047716	$9*(8+7^6-(5^4-3)*2)-1$
970661	$98+(7^6-5)/4*(32+1)$	1051263	$9*((87+6)*(5^4+3)*2-1)$
970818	$-9+(8+(7^6-5)/4)*(32+1)$	1051281	$9*((87+6)*(5^4+3)*2+1)$
970836	$9+(8+(7^6-5)/4)*(32+1)$	1056269	$9*(-8+7^6-5^4*(3+2-1))$
973797	$(98+(7^6-5)/4)*(32+1)$	1056413	$9*(8+7^6-5^4*(3+2-1))$
976914	$-9+8*7*(6*5^4*3-21)$	1056705	$9*(-8+7^6-5^4/3-21)$
976932	$9+8*7*(6*5^4*3-21)$	1056759	$-9+8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*(4+32^{\wedge-1})$
977610	$-9+8*7*(6*(5^4*3-2)-1)$	1056777	$9+8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*(4+32^{\wedge-1})$
977628	$9+8*7*(6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$	1056849	$9*(8+7^6-5^4/3-21)$
977784	$-9+8*7*(6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$	1057083	$9*(-8+7^6-5^4/3+21)$
977802	$9+8*7*(6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$	1057218	$(-9+8*7)*6*(5^4*3^2-1)$
978498	$9+8*7*(6*5^4*3-2-1)$	1057227	$9*(8+7^6-5^4/3+21)$
979716	$9+8*7*(6*(5^4*3+2)-1)$	1057547	$(-9+8*7)*(6*5^4*3^2+1)$
982268	$9*(-8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^3^{\wedge}2)-1$	1057782	$(-9+8*7)*6*(5^4*3^2+1)$
982270	$9*(-8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^3^{\wedge}2)+1$	1058388	$9+(8+(7^6-5^4)*3)*(2+1)$
982412	$9*(8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^3^{\wedge}2)-1$	1058503	$-9-8+7^6*(5+4)-321$
982414	$9*(8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^3^{\wedge}2)+1$	1058521	$9-8+7^6*(5+4)-321$
984062	$(9+8)*((7^6-5^4*3)/2-1)$	1058537	$9+8+7^6*(5+4)-321$
984096	$(9+8)*((7^6-5^4*3)/2+1)$	1059145	$-9-8+7^6*(5+4)+321$
989703	$-9+8*7*6*(5^4*3+21)$	1059161	$-9+8+7^6*(5+4)+321$
989721	$9+8*7*6*(5^4*3+21)$	1059179	$9+8+7^6*(5+4)+321$
990065	$9+8*(7+6*5^4*(32+1))$	1059360	$9+(8+(7^6+5^4)*3)*(2+1)$
993870	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5+(4^3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	1060455	$9*(-8+7^6+5^4/3-21)$
995384	$(9+8)*((7^6-5^4)/2-1)$	1060599	$9*(8+7^6+5^4/3-21)$
996786	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5+(4^3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	1060833	$9*(-8+7^6+5^4/3+21)$
997991	$-9+(876-5^4*3)^2-1$	1060977	$9*(8+7^6+5^4/3+21)$
997993	$-9+(876-5^4*3)^2+1$	1061269	$9*(-8+7^6+5^4*(3+2-1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1061413	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6)+5^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1)$	1169832	$(9+8*76)*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$
1069964	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)-1$	1170142	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1069966	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)+1$	1173913	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5/4-321)$
1070072	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)-1$	1173931	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5/4-321)$
1070074	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)+1$	1175264	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5)/(4/3)^{\wedge}2-1$
1070108	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)-1$	1175266	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5)/(4/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
1070110	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)+1$	1175589	$9+(8+7)*6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$
1070216	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)-1$	1175852	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1070218	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)+1$	1175995	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5/4-3^*21)$
1074528	$9^*8*(-76+5^{\wedge}4*(3+21))$	1176048	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1075833	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$	1176160	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*5/4-321$
1075977	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$	1176178	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*5/4-321$
1077408	$9^*8*7*6*(5^{\wedge}4/3+21)$	1176251	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5/4-32+1)$
1077704	$(9/(8+(7*6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	1176382	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1079226	$-9^*(87-6*5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	1176598	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1079271	$-9^*(87-6*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1))$	1176802	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*5/4+321$
1079811	$-9^*(8+7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1))$	1176820	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*5/4+321$
1079919	$-9^*(8+7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1))$	1176932	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1079937	$-9^*(8-7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1))$	1177003	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5/4+3*21)$
1080729	$9^*(87+6*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1))$	1177128	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1084673	$9-8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$	1177461	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$
1085345	$9+8*7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$	1177605	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$
1085472	$9^*8*(76+5^{\wedge}4*(3+21))$	1179045	$(98+7)*(6*5^{\wedge}4*3-21)$
1092518	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3^*2)-1$	1179049	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5/4+321)$
1092662	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3^*2)-1$	1179067	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5/4+321)$
1092664	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3^*2)+1$	1182204	$9+(8+7)*(6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$
1096183	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$	1182642	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1096201	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$	1182838	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1101175	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	1183455	$(98+7)*(6*5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$
1101191	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	1184012	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5)/(4/3)^{\wedge}2-1$
1101193	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	1184014	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5)/(4/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
1101209	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	1186929	$9+(8+7)*6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$
1101793	$-98*(7-6*5^{\wedge}4*3)-21$	1194480	$(98+7)*6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$
1101835	$-98*(7-6*5^{\wedge}4*3)+21$	1207224	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*(5*(4-3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
1102446	$9+((8+76)*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$	1211896	$(9+8)*((7/(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}-2-1)$
1102554	$-9+((8+76)*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$	1211930	$(9+8)*((7/(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}-2+1)$
1103165	$98*(7+6*5^{\wedge}4*3)-21$	1220175	$-9*(8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*(32-1)))$
1106183	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$	1220553	$-9+((87+6)*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$
1106201	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$	1220571	$9+((87+6)*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$
1111154	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)/3^{\wedge}2+1)$	1220679	$-9+((87+6)*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$
1112967	$-9*(87-6*5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$	1220931	$-9*(8-7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1)))$
1114533	$9^*(87+6*5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$	1225923	$(-9+8*7*6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3^*2-1)$
1115654	$-9-(8/(7-(65^{\wedge}4-3)/2))^{\wedge}-1$	1226577	$(-9+8*7*6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3^*2+1)$
1115672	$9-(8/(7-(65^{\wedge}4-3)/2))^{\wedge}-1$	1230009	$9^*((8-7/6)*5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$
1119617	$9-8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	1233288	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
1119663	$-9-8*(7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*32)-1)$	1238904	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$
1120289	$9+8*7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	1238922	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$
1120335	$-9+8*(7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*32)+1)$	1239947	$9+(8*7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$
1120337	$9+8*(7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*32)-1)$	1239956	$-9*(8+7*(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
1120353	$9+8*(7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*32)+1)$	1239958	$-9*(8+7*(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
1127278	$-9*8+7*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3-2))-1$	1240100	$9*(8-7*(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
1127422	$9*8+7*((6+5)^{\wedge}(4+3-2))-1$	1243108	$(9+8)*((7+6)*5^{\wedge}4/3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1135704	$(-9+8*76)*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$	1243142	$(9+8)*((7+6)*5^{\wedge}4/3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1138767	$-9+8*(76*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2)-1)$	1243917	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5*4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$
1138783	$-9+8*(76*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2)+1)$	1244403	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
1138785	$9+8*(76*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2)-1)$	1244538	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$
1138801	$9+8*(76*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2)+1)$	1251666	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1139705	$9+8*76*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	1254817	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4/3-21)$
1140313	$9+8*76*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	1255153	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4/3+21)$
1141199	$-9+8*(76*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2)-1)$	1256183	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3^*21)$
1141215	$-9+8*(76*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2)+1)$	1256201	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3^*21)$
1141217	$9+8*(76*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2)-1)$	1259487	$-9*(8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*32+1))$
1141233	$9+8*(76*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2)+1)$	1259541	$-9*(8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*32)+1)$
1147689	$-9*(8-76)*5^{\wedge}4*3-21$	1260243	$-9*(8-7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*32-1))$
1150953	$9^*(8*76*(5^{\wedge}4/3+2)+1)$	1265000	$(9/((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$
1154673	$9-8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$	1266250	$(9/((8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$
1155345	$9+8*7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$	1278802	$98*(-7-6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
1159611	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3)/21)$	1280376	$-9*(8-76*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2-1))$
1160019	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(3-21))$	1281051	$-9*(8-76*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2)+1)$
1160163	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(3-21))$	1281069	$-9*(8-76*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2)-1)$
1160352	$-9*(8-76)*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$	1281350	$98*(7+6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
1165096	$(9/8/(7+6+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	1281744	$-9*(8-76*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2+1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1282086	$-9*(8-76*(5^4*3-2^{\wedge}1))$	1340059	$(9+8)*7*(6*(5^4*3+2)-1)$
1282239	$-9*(8-76*5^4*3+21)$	1340161	$(9+8)*(7*6*(5^4*3+2)-1)$
1282509	$9*(-8+(76*5^4+3)*(2+1))$	1340195	$(9+8)*(7*6*(5^4*3+2)+1)$
1282617	$-9*(8-76*5^4*3-21)$	1342206	$-9/8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$
1282770	$-9*(8-76*(5^4*3+2^{\wedge}1))$	1343799	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4(4+3))^*2-1)$
1283130	$9-(8/76-5)*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1343833	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4(4+3))^*2+1)$
1283787	$-9*(8-76*(5^4*3+2)+1)$	1352808	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3-2^{\wedge}1)$
1283805	$-9*(8-76*(5^4*3+2)-1)$	1352834	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3-2^{\wedge}1)$
1284480	$-9*(8-76*(5^4*3+2+1))$	1352949	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4*3-2^{\wedge}1)$
1285564	$-98*(7-6*5^4*(3+2^{\wedge}1))$	1352978	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3-2^{\wedge}1)$
1286201	$98*((7*6*5^4-3)/2+1)$	1358457	$9+8*(7+6)*(5^4-3)*21$
1287377	$98*(7*(6*5^4+3)/2+1)$	1364946	$9+(8*(7+6)*5^4-3)*21$
1289280	$(98*7-6)*(5^4*3+21)$	1365408	$9*((87-6)*(5^4*3-2)-1)$
1290317	$98*(7*(6+5^4*3)-2^{\wedge}1)$	1365426	$9*((87-6)*(5^4*3-2)+1)$
1290415	$98*(7*(6+5^4*3)+2^{\wedge}1)$	1365513	$9+8*((7+6)*5^4+3)*21$
1291150	$98*(-7-6+(5^4+3)*21)$	1368324	$9*((87-6)*(5^4*3+2)-1)$
1293405	$(9+8*7*6)*(5^4*3*2-1)$	1368342	$9*((87-6)*(5^4*3+2)+1)$
1293698	$98*(7+6+(5^4+3)*21)$	1369764	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$
1294012	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3-2+1)$	1369774	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
1294266	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+3*2+1)$	1371561	$9+8*(7+6)*(5^4+3)*21$
1296936	$9*(8+7*6*(5^4*3+2+1))$	1372550	$(9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+3))/(-2-1)$
1298925	$-9*(8+7*(6-5^4*(32+1)))$	1372556	$(9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+3))/(2+1)$
1302831	$-9*876+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1389528	$9*8*(-76+5^4*(32-1))$
1302841	$-9*876+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1404488	$(9/8*(7+6*5^4/3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}1$
1307212	$(9/(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*4*(3+2)))^{\wedge}1$	1410592	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6-5^4*3*21)$
1308664	$9/(-8+(76*5+4/3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}1$	1411123	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5^4)*3/2-1)$
1308808	$9/(8+(76*5+4/3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}1$	1411157	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5^4)*3/2+1)$
1309830	$-9-876+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1411467	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4/3-21)$
1309840	$-9-876+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1411669	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4+3)-21$
1309848	$9-876+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1411907	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4+3)+21$
1309858	$9-876+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1412453	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5^4)*3/2+1)$
1310157	$-9*(8*7+6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1413144	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6+5^4*3*21)$
1310167	$-9*(8*7+6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1415979	$9*((8+7*6)*(5^4*3-2)-1)$
1310265	$-9*(8+7*6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1415979	$9*((8+7*6)*(5^4*3-2)+1)$
1310275	$-9*(8+7*6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1417427	$9*(-8+7*6*5^4*3*2)-1$
1310419	$9*(8-7*6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1417429	$9*(-8+7*6*5^4*3*2)+1$
1310526	$-9*(8+7*6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1417571	$9*(8+7*6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3*2)-1$
1310536	$-9*(8+7*6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1417573	$9*(8+7*6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3*2)+1$
1310937	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5/4+3/21)$	1419003	$9*((8+7*6)*(5^4*3+2)-1)$
1310955	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5/4+3/21)$	1419021	$9*((8+7*6)*(5^4*3+2)+1)$
1310958	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1428544	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4+3)-2-1)$
1310968	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1428570	$9*(87-6/5)*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
1311021	$-9*(8-7*6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1428646	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4+3)+2+1)$
1311031	$-9*(8-7*6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1432255	$(9+8*7/6)/(5^{\wedge}4(4+3)-2)^{\wedge}1$
1311165	$9*(8+7*6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1434456	$9*8*(-76+5^4*3*2-1)$
1311175	$9*(8+7*6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1434519	$9*(8*(-76+5^4*3*2)-1)$
1311273	$9*(8*7+6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1434600	$9*8*(-76+5^4*3*2+1)$
1311283	$9*(8*7+6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1439907	$9*(8*(-7/6+5^4*3*2)-1)$
1311582	$-9+876+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1439925	$9*(8*(-7/6+5^4*3*2)+1)$
1311592	$-9+876+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1440927	$9*(8*(7+6+5^4*3*2)-1)$
1311600	$9+876+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1440945	$9*(8*(7+6+5^4*3*2)+1)$
1311610	$9+876+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1441041	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4/3*2-1)$
1312032	$(98*7+6)*(5^4*3+21)$	1441237	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4/3*2+1)$
1318609	$9*876+5*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1445400	$9*8*(76+5^4*3*2-1)$
1323422	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(3+2))-1$	1445463	$9*(8*(76+5^4*3*2)-1)$
1323424	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(3+2))+1$	1445481	$9*(8*(76+5^4*3*2)+1)$
1326255	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5^4)/3*2-1)$	1445544	$9*8*(76+5^4*3*2+1)$
1326289	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5^4)/3*2+1)$	1463406	$9*87*(-6+5^4*3*2)-21$
1333327	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)/3*2-1)$	1463448	$9*87*(-6+5^4*3*2)+21$
1333395	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4/3*2-1)$	1467594	$-9-87*(6-5^4*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
1333429	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4/3*2+1)$	1468638	$-9+87*(6+5^4*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
1333565	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5^4)/3*2-1)$	1470452	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3+2^{\wedge}1)$
1337203	$(9+8)*7*(6*(5^4*3-2)-1)$	1470478	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3+2^{\wedge}1)$
1337305	$(9+8)*7*(6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$	1470603	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4*3+2^{\wedge}1)$
1337339	$(9+8)*7*(6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$	1470622	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3+2^{\wedge}1)$
1337441	$(9+8)*7*(6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$	1470648	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3+2^{\wedge}1)$
1338318	$9+(8/76+5)*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1470747	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4*3+2^{\wedge}1)$
1338699	$(9+8)*(7*6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3-2-1)$	1470773	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4*3+2^{\wedge}1)$
1338733	$(9+8)*(7*6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3-2+1)$	1472634	$9*(87*(6+5^4*3)-21)$
1338767	$(9+8)*(7*6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3+2-1)$	1472796	$9*(87*(6+5^4*3)-2-1)$
1338971	$(9+8)*(7*(6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3+2)-1)$	1472802	$9*87*(6+5^4*3)-21$
1339005	$(9+8)*(7*(6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3+2)+1)$	1472814	$9*(87*(6+5^4*3)-2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1472844	$9*87*(6+5^4*3)+21$	1646909	$-9-8*(7^6*(5/4-3)+21)$
1472850	$9*(87*(6+5^4*3)+2+1)$	1646927	$9-8*(7^6*(5/4-3)+21)$
1473012	$9*(87*(6+5^4*3)+21)$	1647245	$-9-8*(7^6*(5/4-3)-21)$
1474398	$9*(87*(6+5^4*3+2)+1)$	1647263	$9-8*(7^6*(5/4-3)-21)$
1479528	$9*8*(-76+5^4*(32+1))$	1649634	$98*(-7*6+5^4*3^(2+1))$
1490188	$(98+7^6*(5-43))/(-2-1)$	1651692	$(-98+7*6/5^4-4*3)*21$
1490227	$9-(8+7^6*(5-43))/(2+1)$	1653927	$9+(8+7*6/5^4-4*3)*21$
1490472	$9*8*(76+5^4*(32+1))$	1655808	$(98+7*6/5^4-4*3)*21$
1495944	$(9*87+6)*(5^4*3+21)$	1657866	$98*(7*6+5^4*3^(2+1))$
1496178	$-9*(8-76*5^4*(3+2^4-1))$	1658259	$9*(876*(5^4/3+2)-1)$
1499910	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)/4*3-2-1)$	1658267	$9*876*(5^4/3+2)-1$
1499944	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)/4*3-2+1)$	1658268	$9*876*(5^4/3+2)^4$
1499978	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)/4*3+2-1)$	1658269	$9*876*(5^4/3+2)+1$
1500097	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)/4*3+2^4-1)$	1658277	$9*(876*(5^4/3+2)+1)$
1512557	$9*(-8+7^6*5/(4+3)*2)-1$	1666152	$9*876*(5^4/3+2+1)$
1512559	$9*(-8+7^6*5/(4+3)*2)+1$	1686198	$(-98+(7^6-5)*43)/(2+1)$
1512701	$9*(8+7^6*5/(4+3)*2)-1$	1686219	$-9-(8-(7^6-5)*43)/(2+1)$
1512703	$9*(8+7^6*5/(4+3)*2)+1$	1686237	$9-(8-(7^6-5)*43)/(2+1)$
1520513	$9*8+(7-6/5)*(4^3^2+1)$	1686276	$-98+(7^6+5)*43/(2+1)$
1520539	$98+(7-6/5)*(4^3^2+1)$	1686472	$98+(7^6+5)*43/(2+1)$
1528182	$9*(-8+(7+6)*(5^4-3)*21)$	1703910	$(-9+(8+7)/6)*(5-4^3^2-1)$
1534760	$9+876^4(-5+4+3)*2-1$	1710177	$9*(8*(76*5^4+3)/2+1)$
1534762	$9+876^4(-5+4+3)*2+1$	1712343	$9-87*((6-5-4)^3^2+1)$
1536120	$9*(-8+((7+6)*5^4+3)*21)$	1712517	$9-87*((6-5-4)^3^2-1)$
1542510	$(9/(8-7^6*(5-4^3)^2))^4-1$	1713158	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4*3^4(2+1))$
1542924	$9*(-8+(7+6)*(5^4+3)*21)$	1756250	$(9+(8*7)^4(-6+5+4))*3^4(2+1)$
1552705	$(9-8/(7+6)*5)*(4^3^2+1)$	1762677	$(-98+7^6*5/(4+3))*21$
1567692	$9*((87+6)*(5^4*3-2)-1)$	1766793	$(98+7^6*5/(4+3))*21$
1567710	$9*((87+6)*(5^4*3-2)+1)$	1773577	$9+8^4(-7+6+5)*(432+1)$
1568487	$-9+8*((7^6*5+4)/3-21)$	1780471	$-98-7*(6^4-4^3^2+1)$
1568505	$9+8*((7^6*5+4)/3-21)$	1780485	$-98-7*(6^4-4^3^2-1)$
1568759	$-9+8*(7^6*5+43)/(2+1)$	1780667	$98-7*(6^4-4^3^2+1)$
1568821	$(-9+8*(7^6*5+4^3))/(2+1)$	1780681	$98-7*(6^4-4^3^2-1)$
1568827	$(9+8*(7^6*5+4^3))/(2+1)$	1792742	$(-98+7^6*5^4*3)/21$
1568841	$9+8*((7^6*5+4)/3+21)$	1794296	$(9/8/7*(6-5^4)^4-2)^4-1$
1569186	$9*((87+6)*5^4*3-21)$	1798919	$-9*(8*(7+6^4)-4^3^2)-1$
1569564	$9*((87+6)*5^4*3+21)$	1798921	$-9*(8*(7+6^4)-4^3^2)+1$
1572753	$-9*(8+7)+6*(5+4^3^2-1)$	1799927	$9*(8*(7-6^4)+4^3^2)-1$
1572956	$98+(7-6+5)*(4^3^2-1)$	1799929	$9*(8*(7-6^4)+4^3^2)+1$
1579751	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)*3/2)-1$	1799994	$9+(8+7)*(6*5^4*32-1)$
1579753	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)*3/2)+1$	1800090	$(9+87-6)*(5^4*32+1)$
1579895	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*3/2)-1$	1800099	$9+(8+7)*6*(5^4*32+1)$
1579897	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*3/2)+1$	1804689	$9*(-8*(7+6)+5^4*321)$
1586203	$(-9+8*7)*(6*5^4*3^2-1)$	1804815	$9*((-8-7)*6+5^4*321)$
1586297	$(-9+8*7)*(6*5^4*3^2+1)$	1805067	$9*(-8*7-6+5^4*321)$
1586952	$9*(87+6)*5^4*3+21$	1805541	$9*(-8*7/6+5^4*321)$
1588067	$9*(-8+(7^6-5-4)*3/2)-1$	1805571	$9*(8-7)*(-6+5^4*321)$
1588069	$9*(-8+(7^6-5-4)*3/2)+1$	1805679	$9*(8-7)*(6+5^4*321)$
1588121	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)/4*3^2)-1$	1805709	$9*(8*7/6+5^4*321)$
1588123	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)/4*3^2)+1$	1806183	$9*(8*7+6+5^4*321)$
1588204	$9*(-8+(7^6+5-4)*3/2)+1$	1806435	$9*((8+7)*6+5^4*321)$
1588319	$9*(8+(7^6-5+4)*3/2)-1$	1806561	$9*(8*(7+6)+5^4*321)$
1588400	$9*(8+(7^6+5)/4*3^2)-1$	1815128	$(-98+7^6*5^4)/(3+2^4-1)$
1588402	$9*(8+(7^6+5)/4*3^2)+1$	1815184	$(98+7^6*5^4)/(3+2^4-1)$
1588454	$9*(8+(7^6+5+4)*3/2)-1$	1834448	$-98-7*(65-4^3^2+1)$
1588456	$9*(8+(7^6+5+4)*3/2)+1$	1834454	$-98-7*(65-4^3^2)-1$
1596626	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)*3/2)-1$	1834456	$-98-7*(65-4^3^2)+1$
1596628	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)*3/2)+1$	1834462	$-98-7*(65-4^3^2-1)$
1596770	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3/2)-1$	1834644	$98-7*(65-4^3^2+1)$
1596772	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3/2)+1$	1834650	$98-7*(65-4^3^2)-1$
1606914	$9/8*(7^6+5^4*3^2-1)$	1834652	$98-7*(65-4^3^2)+1$
1618848	$9*876*(5^4/3-2-1)$	1834658	$98-7*(65-4^3^2-1)$
1626723	$9*(876*(5^4/3-2)-1)$	1834889	$98-7*(6*5-4^3^2+1)$
1626731	$9*876*(5^4/3-2)-1$	1835127	$-98+7*(6*5+4^3^2+1)$
1626732	$9*876*(5^4/3-2)^4$	1835176	$98+7*(6+5+4^3^2-1)$
1626733	$9*876*(5^4/3-2)+1$	1835190	$98+7*(6+5+4^3^2+1)$
1626741	$9*(876*(5^4/3-2)+1)$	1835309	$98+7*(6*5+4^3^2-1)$
1638558	$9*876*(5^4/3-2^4-1)$	1835323	$98+7*(6*5+4^3^2+1)$
1642071	$9+876*(5^4*3-2^4-1)$	1835358	$-98+7*(65+4^3^2-1)$
1642929	$-9+876*(5^4*3+2^4-1)$	1835364	$-98+7*(65+4^3^2)-1$
1642947	$9+876*(5^4*3+2^4-1)$	1835366	$-98+7*(65+4^3^2)+1$
1646442	$9*876*(5^4/3+2^4-1)$	1835372	$-98+7*(65+4^3^2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1835554	$98+7*(65+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	1968107	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4\wedge 3-2-1)$
1835560	$98+7*(65+4^3\wedge 2)-1$	1968141	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4\wedge 3-2+1)$
1835562	$98+7*(65+4^3\wedge 2)+1$	1968175	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4\wedge 3+2-1)$
1850835	$(-98+(7^6-5)/4^3)^*21$	1968209	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4\wedge 3+2+1)$
1852380	$-9-(8-(7^6-5)/4)^*3^*21$	1968311	$(9+8)*(7^6-(5^4-3)^*(2+1))$
1852398	$9-(8-(7^6-5)/4)^*3^*21$	1973609	$9*(-8+(7^6-(5^4)^3)^*2)-1$
1852716	$-9-(8-(7^6-5)/4^3)^*21$	1973611	$9*(-8+(7^6-(5^4)^3)^*2)+1$
1852734	$9-(8-(7^6-5)/4^3)^*21$	1973753	$9*(8+(7^6-(5^4)^3)^*2)-1$
1852795	$-98+(7^6-5)/4^3^*21$	1973755	$9*(8+(7^6-(5^4)^3)^*2)+1$
1852991	$98+(7^6-5)/4^3^*21$	1978664	$(9+8)*(7^6-(5^4+3)^*2-1)$
1853052	$-9+(8+(7^6-5)/4^3)^*21$	1978698	$(9+8)*(7^6-(5^4+3)^*2+1)$
1853070	$9+(8+(7^6-5)/4^3)^*21$	1978868	$(9+8)*(7^6-(5^4-3)^*2-1)$
1853388	$-9+(8+(7^6-5)/4)^*3^*21$	1978902	$(9+8)*(7^6-(5^4-3)^*2+1)$
1853406	$9+(8+(7^6-5)/4)^*3^*21$	1991703	$(-98+7^6/5)^*(43^*2-1)$
1854951	$(98+(7^6-5)/4^3)^*21$	1994712	$(9+8)*(7^6-(5^4+3)/2+1)$
1855516	$(9+8)*((7+6)^5-4^3\wedge 2-1)$	1999344	$-9-(8-7^6/5)^*(4^3+21)$
1855550	$(9+8)*((7+6)^5-4^3\wedge 2+1)$	1999362	$9-(8-7^6/5)^*(4^3+21)$
1872491	$-9+8^*7/6/5^{\wedge}4^*321$	2000361	$9+8*((7/(6/54))^3-2-1)$
1872509	$9+8^*7/6/5^{\wedge}4^*321$	2000409	$9+8*((7/(6/54))^3+2+1)$
1873697	$9+8*((7^6-543)^*2-1)$	2000535	$-9+8*((7/(6/54))^3+21)$
1878945	$9+8*((7^6-5^43)^*2-1)$	2000553	$9+8*((7/(6/54))^3+21)$
1879793	$9+8*((7^6-54^3)^*2-1)$	2000704	$-9+(8+7^6/5)^*(4^3+21)$
1881471	$-9+8*((7^6-54-3)^*2+1)$	2000722	$9+(8+7^6/5)^*(4^3+21)$
1881473	$9+8*((7^6-54-3)^*2-1)$	2005354	$(9+8)*(7^6+(5^4+3)/2-1)$
1881567	$-9+8*((7^6-54+3)^*2+1)$	2008363	$(98+7^6/5)^*(43^*2-1)$
1881569	$9+8*((7^6-54+3)^*2-1)$	2008434	$(9-87/65)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
1881615	$-9+8*((7^6-5-43)^*2+1)$	2009763	$(9-8/(7-6+5))^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
1881617	$9+8*((7^6-5-43)^*2-1)$	2012049	$9*87*((6^5-4)/3-21)$
1881777	$9+8*((7^6+5-43)^*2-1)$	2014137	$9*87*((6^5+4)/3-21)$
1881974	$(-9+8*(7^6/5-4))^*(3^2+1)$	2016813	$(-9+8*7^6*5/(4+3))^*(2+1)$
1882097	$9+8*((7^6-54/3)^*2-1)$	2016867	$(9+8*7^6*5/(4+3))^*(2+1)$
1882154	$(9+8*(7^6/5-4))^*(3^2+1)$	2017477	$98*(7/-6+5^4)^*(32+1)$
1882233	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^*(4/3)^2)+1$	2019225	$(9-8/(7/6+5))^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
1882535	$9*(8+(7^6+5)^*(4/3)^2)-1$	2021164	$(9+8)*(7^6+(5^4-3)^*2-1)$
1882561	$9-8*(7^6*(5-4-3)-21)$	2021198	$(9+8)*(7^6+(5^4-3)^*2+1)$
1882614	$(-9+8*(7^6/5+4))^*(3^2+1)$	2021368	$(9+8)*(7^6+(5^4+3)^*2-1)$
1882671	$-9+8*((7^6+54/3)^*2+1)$	2021402	$(9+8)*(7^6+(5^4+3)^*2+1)$
1882794	$(9+8*(7^6/5+4))^*(3^2+1)$	2025023	$98*((7/6+5^4)^*(32+1))$
1882991	$-9+8*((7^6-5+43)^*2+1)$	2031755	$(9+8)*(7^6+(5^4-3)^*(2+1))$
1882993	$9+8*((7^6-5+43)^*2-1)$	2031857	$(9+8)*(7^6+5^4\wedge 3-2-1)$
1883153	$9+8*((7^6+5+43)^*2-1)$	2031891	$(9+8)*(7^6+5^4\wedge 3-2+1)$
1883201	$9+8*((7^6+5+4-3)^*2-1)$	2031925	$(9+8)*(7^6+5^4\wedge 3+2-1)$
1883297	$9+8*((7^6+5+4+3)^*2-1)$	2031959	$(9+8)*(7^6+5^4\wedge 3+2+1)$
1884975	$-9+8*((7^6+5+4)^*3)^*2+1$	2032061	$(9+8)*(7^6+(5^4+3)^*(2+1))$
1884977	$9+8*((7^6+5+4)^*3)^*2-1$	2035155	$(9+8)*((7^6-(6+5+4)+3)^2-1)$
1885823	$-9+8*((7^6+5^4)^*3)^*2+1$	2035189	$(9+8)*((7^6-(6+5+4)+3)^2+1)$
1885825	$9+8*((7^6+5^4)^*3)^*2-1$	2042533	$(9+8)*(7^6+5^4*(3+2-1))$
1888833	$9-8*(7-6/5^{\wedge}4^*3)^*21$	2063766	$(9+8)*(7^6+5^4\wedge 3^*2-1)$
1889335	$-98+7*(6^5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2063800	$(9+8)*(7^6+5^4\wedge 3^*2+1)$
1889349	$-98+7*(6^5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2079905	$9+8*(7+6)^*(5^4\wedge 32-1)$
1891071	$-9+8*((7^6+543)^*2+1)$	2080113	$9+8*(7+6)^*(5^4\wedge 32+1)$
1891073	$9+8*((7^6+543)^*2-1)$	2083859	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4\wedge 3)^*2)-1$
1893783	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4\wedge 3)^*(3^2+1)$	2083861	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4\wedge 3)^*2)+1$
1904425	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4\wedge 3)^*(3^2+1)$	2084003	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4\wedge 3)^*2)-1$
1915033	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4\wedge 3)^*(3^2-1)$	2084005	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4\wedge 3)^*2)+1$
1915926	$-9*(8+7^6*(5-43)/21)$	2085033	$(9+8)*(7^6+5^4*(3^2-1))$
1921829	$98*((7^6+5^4)/3/2-1)$	2091015	$-9-8*(765-4^3\wedge 2+1)$
1922025	$98*((7^6+5^4)/3/2+1)$	2091022	$-9-8*(765-4^3\wedge 2)-1$
1927192	$(-9+(8*7^6-5)^*43)/21$	2091024	$-9-8*(765-4^3\wedge 2)+1$
1927285	$(9+8*(7^6+5)^*43)/21$	2091031	$-9-8*(765-4^3\wedge 2-1)$
1928150	$-98*(7+(6-5-4)^3\wedge 2+1)$	2091033	$9-8*(765-4^3\wedge 2+1)$
1928346	$-98*(7+(6-5-4)^3\wedge 2-1)$	2091040	$9-8*(765-4^3\wedge 2)-1$
1936266	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4\wedge 3^*2-1)$	2091042	$9-8*(765-4^3\wedge 2)+1$
1936300	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4\wedge 3^*2+1)$	2091049	$9-8*(765-4^3\wedge 2-1)$
1943757	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)^*(5^4)^3-2+1$	2093513	$9-8*(7^6\wedge 5-4^3\wedge 2+1)$
1944243	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)^*(5^4)^3+2-1$	2093529	$9-8*(7^6\wedge 5-4^3\wedge 2-1)$
1957533	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4\wedge 3)^*(3+2-1)$	2094113	$9-8*(76^5-4^3\wedge 2+1)$
1957596	$9+8^*(6/5^{\wedge}4^*3^*2+1)$	2094129	$9-8*(76^5-4^3\wedge 2-1)$
1965183	$(9+8)*((7^6-(6+5+4)-3)^2-1)$	2094480	$9*8*((7^6-5)/4-321)$
1965217	$(9+8)*((7^6-(6+5+4)-3)^2+1)$	2095675	$(9+8)*(7^6+5^4\wedge 3^*2+1)$
1967121	$(9+8)/7/((6^5)^4-3^2)^{\wedge}1$	2096601	$9-8*(76-5-4^3\wedge 2-1)$
1968005	$(9+8)*(7^6-(5^4+3)^*(2+1))$	2097721	$9+8*(76-5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2100175	$-9+8*(76*5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2118285	$9*(-8+(7^6-5+43)*2-1)$
2100191	$-9+8*(76*5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2118339	$9*(8*(7^6+5)/4+3*21)$
2100193	$9+8*(76*5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2118383	$9*(8+(7^6+5*(4+3))*2)-1$
2100209	$9+8*(76*5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2118385	$9*(8+(7^6+5*(4+3))*2)+1$
2100775	$-9+8*(7*65+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2118483	$9*(-8+(7^6+5+43)*2+1)$
2100791	$-9+8*(7*65+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2118537	$9*(-8+(7^6+5+3)*2+1)$
2100793	$9+8*(7*65+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2118645	$9*(-8+(7^6+5+4+3)*2+1)$
2100809	$9+8*(7*65+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2118653	$-9+8-(7^6+5+4)*3-21$
2103255	$-9+8*(765+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2118655	$9-8-(7^6+5+4)*3-21$
2103262	$-9+8*(765+4^3\wedge 2)-1$	2118815	$9*(8+(7^6-5+4^3)*2)-1$
2103264	$-9+8*(765+4^3\wedge 2)+1$	2118817	$9*(8+(7^6-5+4^3)*2)+1$
2103271	$-9+8*(765+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2118833	$9*(8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2)-1$
2103273	$9+8*(765+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2118835	$9*(8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2)+1$
2103280	$9+8*(765+4^3\wedge 2)-1$	2119887	$9*(8*((7^6-5)/4+32)-1)$
2103282	$9+8*(765+4^3\wedge 2)+1$	2119905	$9*(8*((7^6-5)/4+32)+1)$
2103289	$9+8*(765+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2120067	$9*(8*((7^6+5)/4+32)-1)$
2106305	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4-3)*2)-1$	2120085	$9*(8*((7^6+5)/4+32)+1)$
2106307	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4-3)*2)+1$	2120517	$9*(-8+(7^6+5+4^3)*2-1)$
2106334	$-98-(7^6-5^4)*3-21$	2120535	$9*(-8+(7^6+5+4^3)*2+1)$
2106451	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4-3)*2)+1$	2120679	$9*(8+(7^6+5+4^3)*2+1)$
2106530	$98-(7^6-5^4)*3-21$	2121359	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4/3)*2)-1$
2106557	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4+3)*2)-1$	2121361	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4/3)*2)+1$
2106559	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4+3)*2)+1$	2121471	$9*(-8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2-1)$
2107827	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)*2-1)$	2121489	$9*(-8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2+1)$
2107836	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)*2)+1$	2121503	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4/3)*2)-1$
2107837	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)*2)+1$	2121505	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4/3)*2)+1$
2107845	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)*2+1)$	2121633	$9*(8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2+1)$
2107971	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*2-1)$	2123369	$9*(-8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2)-1$
2107979	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*2)-1$	2123371	$9*(-8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2)+1$
2107980	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*2)+1$	2123513	$9*(8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2)-1$
2107981	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*2)+1$	2123515	$9*(8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2)+1$
2107989	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*2+1)$	2124855	$-9*(8+(7-6/5^4-4^3)*21)$
2111849	$9*(-8+(7^6-5*4^3)*2)-1$	2125400	$9+(8+7/65)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
2111851	$9*(-8+(7^6-5*4^3)*2)+1$	2127033	$9*(87+6/5^4-4^3*21)$
2111993	$9*(8+(7^6-5*4^3)*2)-1$	2127375	$9*(-8+(7^6+5+4^3)*2-1)$
2111995	$9*(8+(7^6-5*4^3)*2)+1$	2127385	$9*(-8+(7^6+5+4^3)*2)+1$
2113731	$9*(-8+(7^6-5*4^3)*2-1)$	2127393	$9*(-8+(7^6+5+4^3)*2+1)$
2113749	$9*(-8+(7^6-5*4^3)*2+1)$	2127501	$9*(-8+(7+6/5^4-4^3)*21)$
2113859	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4/3)*2)-1$	2127519	$9*(8+(7^6+5+4^3)*2-1)$
2113861	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4/3)*2)+1$	2127527	$9*(8+(7^6+5+4^3)*2)-1$
2114003	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4/3)*2)-1$	2127528	$9*(8+(7^6+5+4^3)*2)+1$
2114005	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4/3)*2)+1$	2127529	$9*(8+(7^6+5+4^3)*2)+1$
2114685	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)*2-1)$	2127537	$9*(8+(7^6+5+4^3)*2+1)$
2114703	$9*(8*(7^6-5)/4-321)$	2127645	$9*(8+(7+6/5^4-4^3)*21)$
2114883	$9*(8*(7^6+5)/4-321)$	2128805	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4-3)*2)-1$
2115279	$9*(8*((7^6-5)/4-32)-1)$	2128807	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4-3)*2)+1$
2115297	$9*(8*((7^6-5)/4-32)+1)$	2128834	$-98-(7^6+5^4)*3-21$
2115459	$9*(8*((7^6+5)/4-32)-1)$	2128913	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4+3)*2)-1$
2115477	$9*(8*((7^6+5)/4-32)+1)$	2128951	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4-3)*2)+1$
2116529	$9*(-8+(7^6-5*4^3)*2)-1$	2129030	$98-(7^6+5^4)*3-21$
2116531	$9*(-8+(7^6-5*4^3)*2)+1$	2129057	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4+3)*2)-1$
2116547	$9*(-8+(7^6+5-4^3)*2)-1$	2129059	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4+3)*2)+1$
2116549	$9*(-8+(7^6+5-4^3)*2)+1$	2140704	$9*8*((7^6-5)/4+321)$
2116709	$-9+8-(7^6-5^4)*3-21$	2140884	$9*8*((7^6+5)/4+321)$
2116711	$9-8-(7^6-5^4)*3-21$	2142693	$9*(87+6/5^4-4^3)*21$
2116719	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4-3)*2-1)$	2149517	$-9*8+(7+6/5)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
2116881	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4-3)*2)+1$	2149661	$9*8+(7+6/5)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
2116979	$9*(-8+(7^6-5*(4+3))*2)-1$	2149687	$98+(7+6/5)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
2116981	$9*(-8+(7^6-5*(4+3))*2)+1$	2151361	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4+3)*2)+1$
2117267	$9*(8+(7^6-(5+4)*3)*2)-1$	2151503	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4+3)*2)-1$
2117269	$9*(8+(7^6-(5+4)*3)*2)+1$	2151505	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4+3)*2)+1$
2117422	$-98-(7^6-5-4)*3-21$	2196100	$(-9+(8*7^6-5)*(4+3))/(2+1)$
2117495	$9*(-8+(7^6-5-4/3)*2)-1$	2196106	$(9+(8*7^6-5)*(4+3))/(2+1)$
2117497	$9*(-8+(7^6-5-4/3)*2)+1$	2196194	$98*((7^6+5)^4-3)/21$
2117644	$-9+8+7^6*5^4/3-21$	2196205	$(-9+8*(7^6+5)*(4+3))/(2+1)$
2117720	$9+8+7^6*5^4/3+21$	2196211	$(9+8*(7^6+5)*(4+3))/(2+1)$
2117867	$9*(8+(7^6+5+4/3)*2)-1$	2196222	$98*((7^6+5)^4+3)/21$
2117869	$9*(8+(7^6+5+4/3)*2)+1$	2202116	$98+7^6/5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
2117875	$9*(8+(7^6+5*4/3)*2)+1$	2235138	$-98+(7^6-5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$
2117942	$98-(7^6+5+4)*3-21$	2235164	$-9*8+(7^6-5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$
2118095	$9*(-8+(7^6+(5+4)*3)*2)-1$	2235308	$9*8+(7^6-5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$
2118097	$9*(-8+(7^6+(5+4)*3)*2)+1$	2235354	$9*-8+(7^6+5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2235498	$9^*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^*(3+2)-1)$	2352474	$9^*(8-765+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
2235524	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^*(3+2)-1)$	2352492	$9^*(8-765+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2242779	$(9-8/(7+6+5))^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	2354069	$9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*(3/2+1)$
2246937	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7/6^*5)/((4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	2354193	$-9^*(8^*(76-5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
2250162	$9^*(-8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21)$	2355138	$-9^*(8+7^*65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
2250306	$9^*(8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21)$	2355660	$-9^*((87-6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
2250330	$9^*(-8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)-21$	2355795	$-9^*(8+76^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2250372	$9^*(-8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)+21$	2355813	$-9^*(8+76^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
2250474	$9^*(8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)-21$	2355911	$-9^*(8^*(7^*6+5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2250516	$9^*(8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)+21$	2355913	$-9^*(8^*(7^*6+5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2250540	$9^*(-8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21)$	2356245	$9^*((8-76)^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2250684	$9^*(8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21)$	2356631	$-9^*(8^*(7^*6-5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2261609	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^*2)-1$	2356633	$-9^*(8^*(7^*6-5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2261611	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^*2)+1$	2357333	$-9^*(8+7^*6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2261753	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^*2)-1$	2357335	$-9^*(8+7^*6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2261755	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^*2)+1$	2357477	$9^*(8-7^*6^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2268567	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*(4-3/21)$	2357479	$9^*(8-7^*6^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2268847	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4-3/21)$	2357639	$9^*(8^*(7-6^*5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2269043	$98+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4-3/21)$	2357919	$-9^*(87+65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2269323	$(98+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*(4-3/21)$	2357927	$-9^*(87+65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2286781	$98^*7/6^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$	2357929	$-9^*(87+65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2286908	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	2357937	$-9^*(87+65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2288520	$-9^*(87+6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	2358234	$-9^*(87+6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2288538	$-9^*(87+6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	2358252	$-9^*(87+6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2290086	$9^*(87-6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	2358423	$-9^*(87+6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2290104	$9^*(87-6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	2358486	$-9^*(8+7+6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2302101	$(-9+876^{\wedge}(-5+4+3))^*(2+1)$	2358567	$-9^*(8+7+6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2302531	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$	2358594	$-9^*(8+7+6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2302625	$(9-8/(7+6^*5))^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	2358603	$-9^*(87-6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2302727	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$	2358621	$-9^*(87-6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2304207	$-9^*(8^*765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	2358674	$9^*(8-7^*(6+5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2304215	$-9^*(8^*765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	2358851	$-9^*(8^*(7/6+5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2304217	$-9^*(8^*765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	2358853	$-9^*(8^*(7/6+5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2304225	$-9^*(8^*765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	2359019	$9^*(8^*(7/6+5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2305548	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6/5-4+(3+2)^{\wedge}-1)$	2359097	$-9^*(87-65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2305891	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6/5-(4/3+2)^{\wedge}-1)$	2359099	$-9^*(87-65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2306332	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6/5+4+(3+2)^{\wedge}-1)$	2359493	$9^*(87-65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2308392	$-9^*(87^*65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	2359495	$9^*(87-65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2308400	$-9^*(87^*65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	2359571	$-9^*(8^*(7/6-5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2308402	$-9^*(87^*65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	2359573	$-9^*(8^*(7/6-5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2308410	$-9^*(87^*65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	2359739	$9^*(8^*(7/6+5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2313960	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4/3-21)$	2359741	$9^*(8^*(7/6+5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2315570	$(-9+(8-7)/6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	2359755	$-9^*(8+7-65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2319867	$-9^*(876^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	2359916	$-9^*(8-7^*(6+5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2319875	$-9^*(876^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	2359918	$-9^*(8-7^*(6+5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2319877	$-9^*(876^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	2360376	$9^*(8^*7+65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
2319885	$-9^*(876^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	2360394	$9^*(8^*7+65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2327041	$(9-8/(7+6)/5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	2360655	$9^*(87+65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
2331927	$-9^*(8^*76^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	2360663	$9^*(87+65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2331945	$-9^*(8^*76^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	2360665	$9^*(87+65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2335797	$-9^*(87^*6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	2360673	$9^*(87+65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2335815	$-9^*(87^*6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	2360951	$-9^*(8^*(7-6^*5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2336075	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*4-3/21)$	2360953	$-9^*(8^*(7-6^*5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2336271	$98+7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*4-3/21)$	2361113	$-9^*(8-7^*6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2339811	$9^*(-8+(7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32-1))$	2361115	$-9^*(8-7^*6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2339955	$9^*(8+(7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32-1))$	2361257	$9^*(8+7^*6^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2340045	$9^*(-8+(7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32+1))$	2361259	$9^*(8+7^*6^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2340189	$9^*(8+(7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32+1))$	2362635	$-9^*(8-76^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2342294	$(9+8)^*(7^*(7-6+5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	2362653	$-9^*(8-76^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
2343609	$-9^*(8+7)+6^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	2362679	$9^*(8^*(7^*6+5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2343621	$-9^*(8+7)+6^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	2362681	$9^*(8^*(7^*6+5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
2343879	$9^*(8+7)+6^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	2362932	$9^*((87-6)^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
2343891	$9^*(8+7)+6^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	2362950	$9^*((87-6)^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2344175	$-9^*(8^*7^*6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	2363085	$9^*((8+76)^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2344177	$-9^*(8^*7^*6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	2363310	$-9^*(8-7^*65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2351358	$-9^*(876+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	2363328	$-9^*(8-7^*65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
2351376	$-9^*(876+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	2363490	$9^*((87+6)^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2351448	$-9^*(876-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	2363940	$9^*(87^*6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
2351466	$-9^*(876-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	2363958	$9^*(87^*6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2351909	$9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(3/2+1)$	2364030	$9^*(87^*6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
2352330	$-9^*(8+765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	2364048	$9^*(87^*6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
2352348	$-9^*(8+765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	2364399	$9^*(8^*(76-5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2364417	$9*(8*(76-5)+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2466095	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
2364471	$9*(8*(7+65)+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2466156	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
2364489	$9*(8*(7+65)+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2466352	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
2364714	$9*(8*76-5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2466413	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
2364732	$9*(8*76-5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2466431	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
2364804	$9*(8*76+5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2467692	$9*876*((5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
2364822	$9*(8*76+5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2469271	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4^3)*21$
2365119	$9*(8*(76+5)+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2469467	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4^3)*21$
2365137	$9*(8*(76+5)+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2469796	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5*(4+3))*21$
2366100	$-9*(8-765-4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2469964	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)*3)*21$
2366118	$-9*(8-765-4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2469992	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5*(4+3))*21$
2366244	$9*(8+765+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2470160	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)*3)*21$
2367126	$9*(876-5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2470179	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-54/3)*21$
2367216	$9*(876+5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2470234	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54/3)*21$
2367234	$9*(876+5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2470250	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6-54/3)*21$
2367900	$9*(87*(6+5)+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2470252	$9-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54/3)*21$
2367918	$9*(87*(6+5)+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2470268	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6-54/3)*21$
2368062	$9*((8+7)*65+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2470384	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4^3)*21$
2368080	$9*((8+7)*65+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2470454	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4/3)*21$
2369484	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6)+5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2470516	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5/(4+3))*21$
2369494	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6)+5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2470742	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5/(4+3))*21$
2369628	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6)+5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2470804	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4/3)*21$
2369638	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6)+5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2470867	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4/3)*21$
2369689	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3/21)$	2470874	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4^3)*21$
2369885	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3/21)$	2470990	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)*21$
2374415	$9*(8*7*6*5+4^3\wedge 2)-1$	2471006	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)*21$
2374417	$9*(8*7*6*5+4^3\wedge 2)+1$	2471008	$9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)*21$
2379320	$(-9-8)*(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)/2+1)$	2471024	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)*21$
2379354	$(9+8)*(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)/2+1)$	2471079	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)*21$
2382362	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^3\wedge 2)-1$	2471098	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+(5+4)*3)*21$
2382364	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^3\wedge 2)+1$	2471266	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5*(4+3))*21$
2382383	$-9+(8/(7^{\wedge}6*5^4*3-2))^{\wedge}-1$	2471294	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+(5+4)*3)*21$
2382401	$9+(8/(7^{\wedge}6*5^4*3-2))^{\wedge}-1$	2471462	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5*(4+3))*21$
2382795	$9*(87*6*5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2471791	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4^3)*21$
2386104	$98*((7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2)-1)$	2471987	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4^3)*21$
2386300	$98*((7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2)+1)$	2474827	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
2386665	$9*(8*76*5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2474845	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
2386692	$98*((7+6)*5^{\wedge}4*3-21)$	2474906	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
2391200	$98*((7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2)-1)$	2475102	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
2391569	$(9+8/(7+6)/5)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2475163	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
2398707	$9*(876*5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2475181	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
2398715	$9*(876*5+4^3\wedge 2)-1$	2475795	$(9+8/(7+6+5))*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
2398717	$9*(876*5+4^3\wedge 2)+1$	2477251	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4^3)*21$
2398725	$9*(876*5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2477447	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4^3)*21$
2402950	$(9+(8-7)/6)*(-5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2499918	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(3+2))-1$
2410182	$9*(87*65+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2499952	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(3+2)+1)$
2410190	$9*(87*65+4^3\wedge 2)-1$	2509906	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
2410192	$9*(87*65+4^3\wedge 2)+1$	2510102	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
2410200	$9*(87*65+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2510163	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
2411604	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43/2-1)$	2510181	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
2412005	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43/2-1)$	2520186	$9*(87+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))-21$
2414367	$9*(8*765+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2530575	$(9*(8+7))^{\wedge}-6/(5^{\wedge}-4/-3+2))^{\wedge}-1$
2414375	$9*(8*765+4^3\wedge 2)-1$	2531925	$(9*(8+7))^{\wedge}-6/(5^{\wedge}-4/3+2))^{\wedge}-1$
2414377	$9*(8*765+4^3\wedge 2)+1$	2534687	$(9/(87*(65+4^3\wedge 2)))^{\wedge}-1$
2414385	$9*(8*765+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2539056	$(9-(8+7)/6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1$
2415985	$(9+8/(7+6*5))*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2539069	$(9-(8+7)/6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
2428506	$-9*(87-6^{\wedge}5-4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2546183	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*321)$
2431077	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	2546201	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*321)$
2431095	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	2571399	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)/21)$
2431156	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	2571543	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)/21)$
2431352	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	2621380	$(9+(8-7)^{\wedge}6)*(-5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$
2431413	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	2621500	$(9+(8-7)^{\wedge}6)*(5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$
2431431	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	2627508	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4/3+21)$
2436609	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+3/21)$	2627704	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4/3+21)$
2436917	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3/21)$	2638531	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3)*21$
2437113	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3/21)$	2638727	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3)*21$
2437421	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+3/21)$	2646846	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-43)/2+1)$
2456313	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4^3\wedge 2+1)$	2646998	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4-3)/2)-1$
2456347	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4^3\wedge 2-1)$	2647000	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4-3)/2)+1$
2463811	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4^3)*21$	2647027	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4+3)/2)+1$
2464007	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4^3)*21$	2647178	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4-3)/2)-1$
2466077	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	2647205	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4+3)/2)-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2647207	$9*(8+(7^6*5+4+3)/2)+1$	2823153	$9+8*(7^6-54/3)*(2+1)$
2658595	$(-9-8/7)*(6*5-4^4*3^2-1)$	2823183	$-9+8*((7^6-5-4)*3-21)$
2666773	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*4/3-2-1)$	2823194	$98+(7^6-5*4)*(3+21)$
2666875	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*4/3+2+1)$	2823201	$9+8*((7^6-5-4)*3-21)$
2677483	$(9+8)*(7*6*5^4*3*2-1)$	2823262	$-98+(7^6-5-4)*(3+21)$
2677491	$-9-(8-76)*5^4*3*21$	2823285	$9*(8*(7^6-5*4)/3+21)$
2677509	$9-(8-76)*5^4*3*21$	2823383	$9*-8+(7^6-5)*4*3*2-1$
2677517	$(9+8)*(7*6*5^4*3*2+1)$	2823502	$-98+(7^6+5-4)*(3+21)$
2699385	$(9+8/(7/6+5))*(4^3*2+1)$	2823650	$98+(7^6-5+4)*(3+21)$
2700801	$9*((8+7)*(6+5^4*3^2)-1)$	2823769	$9*8+(7^6+5)*4*3*2+1$
2705808	$-98+7^6*(5^4+3)-21$	2823867	$9*(8*(7^6+5*4)/3-21)$
2705850	$-98+7^6*(5^4+3)+21$	2823890	$98+(7^6+5+4)*(3+21)$
2705884	$9*8+(7^6-5)*(4*3*2-1)$	2823958	$-98+(7^6+5*4)*(3+21)$
2706140	$98+(7^6+5)*(4*3*2-1)$	2823969	$9+8*((7^6+5+4)*3+21)$
2708811	$(9+8/(7-6+5))*(4^3*2-1)$	2823999	$-9+8*(7^6+54/3)*(2+1)$
2710176	$(9+87/65)*(4^3*2+1)$	2824017	$9+8*(7^6+54/3)*(2+1)$
2734228	$-98-7*(6-5^4*3/2)+1$	2824154	$98+(7^6+5*4)*(3+21)$
2734242	$-98-7*(6-5^4*3/2)-1$	2824230	$9+(8*7^6+5*4^3)*(2+1)$
2734508	$98+7*(6+5^4*3/2)-1$	2824245	$9*(8*(7^6+5*4)/3+21)$
2734522	$98+7*(6+5^4*3/2)+1$	2824479	$-9+8*(7^6-5+4^3)*(2+1)$
2745176	$98*(7^6*5+4+3)/21$	2824497	$9+8*(7^6-5+4^3)*(2+1)$
2745442	$98*(7^6*5+4+3)/21$	2824683	$9*(8*(7^6+54)/3-21)$
2778111	$9/8*(7^6-54-3)*21$	2824695	$-9+8*((7^6+54)*3-21)$
2778549	$(-9+8*(7^6-5^4*3))*(2+1)$	2824713	$9+8*(7^6+54)*3-21$
2778603	$(9+8*(7^6-5^4*3))*(2+1)$	2824737	$9+8*(7^6+5+4^3)*(2+1)$
2784537	$9/8*(7^6+5^4*3)*21$	2824809	$9+8*(7^6+54-3)*(2+1)$
2791353	$9*(8^7/6-5^4*3*21)$	2824857	$9+8*((7^6+54)*3-2-1)$
2799860	$(98+7*6)*(5^4*3^2-1)$	2824867	$-9+8*((7^6+54)*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
2800140	$(98+7*6)*(5^4*3^2+1)$	2824877	$9+8*((7^6+54)*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
2808387	$9*(8*(7^6-5^4)/3-21)$	2824885	$9+8*((7^6+54)*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
2808399	$-9+8*((7^6-5^4)*3-21)$	2824887	$-9+8*((7^6+54)*3+2+1)$
2808417	$9+8*((7^6-5^4)*3-21)$	2824905	$9+8*((7^6+54)*3+2+1)$
2808478	$-98+(7^6-5^4)*(3+21)$	2824953	$9+8*(7^6+54+3)*(2+1)$
2808674	$98+(7^6-5^4)*(3+21)$	2825031	$-9+8*((7^6+54)*3+21)$
2808735	$-9+8*((7^6-5^4)*3+21)$	2825049	$9+8*((7^6+54)*3+21)$
2808753	$9+8*((7^6-5^4)*3+21)$	2825061	$9*(8*(7^6+54)/3+21)$
2808765	$9*(8*(7^6-5^4)/3+21)$	2825196	$-9+(8*7^6+54^3)*(2+1)$
2810535	$-9+8*(7^6-54^3)*(2+1)$	2825214	$9+(8*7^6+54^3)*(2+1)$
2810553	$9+8*(7^6-54^3)*(2+1)$	2825262	$9*((8*7^6+5^4)/3-21)$
2818425	$9+8*(7^6-5^4*3)*(2+1)$	2825640	$9*((8*7^6+5^4)/3+21)$
2818549	$(-9+8*(7^6-5^4/3))*(2+1)$	2826384	$9*8*((7^6+54)/3+21)$
2818603	$(9+8*(7^6-5^4/3))*(2+1)$	2827455	$-9+8*(7^6+54^3)*(2+1)$
2819697	$9+8*(7^6-54^3)*(2+1)$	2827473	$9+8*(7^6+54^3)*(2+1)$
2820768	$9*8*((7^6-54)/3-21)$	2827791	$9^{\wedge}(8+7-6-5)*(432-1)$
2821512	$9*((8*7^6-5^4)/3-21)$	2828549	$(-9+8*(7^6+5^4/3))*(2+1)$
2821890	$9*((8*7^6-5^4)/3+21)$	2828603	$(9+8*(7^6+5^4/3))*(2+1)$
2821938	$-9+(8*7^6-54^3)*(2+1)$	2828727	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)*(2+1)$
2821956	$9+(8*7^6-54^3)*(2+1)$	2828745	$9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)*(2+1)$
2822091	$9*(8*(7^6-54)/3-21)$	2836599	$-9+8*(7^6+54^3)*(2+1)$
2822103	$-9+8*((7^6-54)*3-21)$	2836617	$9+8*(7^6+54^3)*(2+1)$
2822121	$9+8*((7^6-54)*3-21)$	2838387	$9*(8*(7^6+5^4)/3-21)$
2822199	$-9+8*(7^6-54-3)*(2+1)$	2838399	$-9+8*((7^6+5^4)*3-21)$
2822217	$9+8*(7^6-54-3)*(2+1)$	2838417	$9+8*((7^6+5^4)*3-21)$
2822265	$9+8*((7^6-54)*3-2-1)$	2838478	$-98+(7^6+5^4)*(3+21)$
2822267	$-9+8*((7^6-54)*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	2838674	$98+(7^6+5^4)*(3+21)$
2822275	$-9+8*((7^6-54)*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	2838735	$-9+8*((7^6+5^4)*3+21)$
2822285	$9+8*((7^6-54)*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	2838753	$9+8*((7^6+5^4)*3+21)$
2822293	$9+8*((7^6-54)*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	2838765	$9*(8*(7^6+5^4)/3+21)$
2822295	$-9+8*((7^6-54)*3+2+1)$	2840913	$9^{\wedge}(8+7-6-5)*(432+1)$
2822313	$9+8*((7^6-54)*3+2+1)$	2857173	$(9+8)*(7^6*5/(4+3))^2-1$
2822343	$-9+8*(7^6-54+3)*(2+1)$	2857207	$(9+8)*(7^6*5/(4+3))^2+1$
2822361	$9+8*(7^6-54+3)*(2+1)$	2864394	$9*(-8+7^6+5^4*3^2)$
2822415	$-9+8*(7^6-5-4^3)*(2+1)$	2864538	$9*(8+7^6+5^4*3^2)$
2822433	$9+8*(7^6-5-4^3)*(2+1)$	2868549	$(-9+8*(7^6+5^4*3))*(2+1)$
2822439	$-9+8*((7^6-54)*3+21)$	2868603	$(9+8*(7^6+5^4*3))*(2+1)$
2822457	$9+8*((7^6-54)*3+21)$	2869759	$((9^{\wedge}8-7+6)/5-4)/3-21$
2822469	$9*(8*(7^6-54)/3+21)$	2869801	$((9^{\wedge}8-7+6)/5-4)/3+21$
2822673	$9+8*(7^6+5-4^3)*(2+1)$	2873924	$9*(-8+7^6*(5/(4+3)+2))-1$
2822907	$9*(8*(7^6-5^4)/3-21)$	2873926	$9*(-8+7^6*(5/(4+3)+2))+1$
2822940	$9+(8*7^6-5^4*3)*(2+1)$	2874068	$9*(8+7^6*(5/(4+3)+2))-1$
2822998	$-98+(7^6-5^4)*(3+21)$	2874070	$9*(8+7^6*(5/(4+3)+2))+1$
2823135	$-9+8*(7^6-54/3)*(2+1)$	2876349	$98*((7^6+5)/4-3*21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2877605	$((9^8+7^8)/5+4)/3-21$	2939393	$9^8+7^*((6^5/4/3)^2-1)$
2877647	$((9^8+7^8)/5+4)/3+21$	2939407	$9^8+7^*((6^5/4/3)^2+1)$
2879044	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-32-1)$	2939433	$98+7^*((6^5/4/3)^2+1)$
2879141	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-32)-1$	2941198	$98+(7^6-5)^*(4^3*2+1)$
2879142	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-32)^{\wedge}1$	2941422	$9^8+(7^6+5)^*(4^3*2+1)$
2879143	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-32)+1$	2941448	$98+(7^6+5)^*(4^3*2+1)$
2879240	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-32+1)$	2945103	$9^8^{7/6-5^4*321}$
2879289	$98^*((7^6+5)/4-32-1)$	2959852	$(9^8+76)^*(5^4*32-1)$
2879386	$98^*((7^6+5)/4-32)-1$	2960103	$9^*(8^7/6-5^4*(32+1))$
2879387	$98^*((7^6+5)/4-32)^{\wedge}1$	2960148	$(9^8+76)^*(5^4*32+1)$
2879388	$98^*((7^6+5)/4-32)+1$	2965719	$9^*(8^7/6-5^4*32-1)$
2879485	$98^*((7^6+5)/4-32+1)$	2965737	$9^*(8^7/6-5^4*32+1)$
2879632	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	2971353	$9^*(8^7/6-5^4*(32-1))$
2879877	$98^*((7^6+5)/4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	2974767	$-9^*(8+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)/21)$
2879926	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-3-21)$	2974911	$9^*(8-7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)/21)$
2880171	$98^*((7^6+5)/4-3-21)$	2984095	$(9+8)^*((7^6-5^4)^3/2-1)$
2880514	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+3-21)$	2984129	$(9+8)^*((7^6-5^4)^3/2+1)$
2880759	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+3-21)$	2999803	$(9+8)^*((7^6-5-4)^3/2-1)$
2881298	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-3^2-1)$	2999905	$(9+8)^*((7^6-5)/4^3*2-1)$
2881494	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-3^2+1)$	3000007	$(9+8)^*((7^6-5+4)^3/2-1)$
2881543	$98^*((7^6+5)/4-3^2-1)$	3000092	$(9+8)^*((7^6+5-4)^3/2+1)$
2881592	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-3^2-1)$	3000194	$(9+8)^*((7^6+5)/4^3*2+1)$
2881739	$98^*((7^6+5)/4-3^2+1)$	3000262	$(9+8)^*((7^6+5+4)^3/2-1)$
2881963	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-3)-21$	3000296	$(9+8)^*((7^6+5+4)^3/2+1)$
2882005	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-3)+21$	3014587	$(9+(8+7)/6)^*(-5+4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
2882208	$98^*((7^6+5)/4-3)-21$	3014610	$(9+(8+7)/6)^*(-5+4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
2882250	$98^*((7^6+5)/4-3)+21$	3015970	$(9+8)^*((7^6+5^4)^3/2-1)$
2882264	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-3/21)$	3016004	$(9+8)^*((7^6+5^4)^3/2+1)$
2882292	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+3/21)$	3027036	$9^*(8^7/6-(5^4+3)^*21)$
2882509	$98^*((7^6+5)/4-3/21)$	3028170	$9^*(8^7/6-(5^4-3)^*21)$
2882537	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+3/21)$	3044478	$9^*(8^7/6+5^4*(3-21))$
2882551	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+3)-21$	3070782	$(9-87)^*(6-5^4*3^*21)$
2882593	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+3)+21$	3071718	$(-9+87)^*(6+5^4*3^*21)$
2882796	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+3)-21$	3087686	$98^7*((6+5^4/3)^*21)$
2882838	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+3)+21$	3092497	$9+8^7*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3)/21$
2883062	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+3^2-1)$	3124375	$-9-8^*(76-5^4*(3/2)+1)$
2883258	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+3^2+1)$	3124391	$-9-8^*(76-5^4*(3/2)-1)$
2883307	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+3^2-1)$	3124393	$9-8^*(76-5^4*(3/2)+1)$
2883438	$-9^*(8+7)+(6+5)^*(4^3^2-1)$	3124409	$9-8^*(76-5^4*(3/2)-1)$
2883460	$-9^*(8+7)+(6+5)^*(4^3^2+1)$	3125591	$-9+8^*(76+5^4*(3/2)-1)$
2883503	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+3^2+1)$	3125607	$-9+8^*(76+5^4*(3/2)+1)$
2883708	$9^*(8+7)+(6+5)^*(4^3^2-1)$	3125609	$9+8^*(76+5^4*(3/2)-1)$
2884042	$98^*((7^6-5)/4-3+21)$	3125625	$9+8^*(76+5^4*(3/2)+1)$
2884287	$98^*((7^6+5)/4-3+21)$	3126030	$9^*(-8+7^6*(5-43/21))$
2884630	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+3+21)$	3126174	$9^*(8+7^6*(5-43/21))$
2884875	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+3+21)$	3128664	$9^*(8^7/6-5^4*3-21)$
2884924	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	3144042	$9^*(8^7/6-5^4/3+21)$
2885169	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	3157839	$9^*87/65*(4^3^2+1)$
2885316	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+32-1)$	3159387	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3-21)$
2885413	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+32)-1$	3159531	$9^*(8+(7^6-5^4)^3-21)$
2885414	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+32)^{\wedge}1$	3159765	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3+21)$
2885415	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+32)+1$	3159909	$9^*(8+(7^6-5^4)^3+21)$
2885512	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+32+1)$	3161790	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3*(2+1))$
2885561	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+32-1)$	3162792	$9^*(8^7/6+5^4*3+21)$
2885658	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+32)-1$	3165905	$(9+8/(7+6))^5*(4^3^2+1)$
2885659	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+32)^{\wedge}1$	3170646	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3*(2+1))$
2885660	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+32)+1$	3170790	$9^*(8+(7^6-5^4)^3*(2+1))$
2885757	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+32+1)$	3172077	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3*(2+1))$
2888452	$98^*((7^6-5)/4+3^*21)$	3172221	$9^*(8+(7^6-5^4)^3*(2+1))$
2888697	$98^*((7^6+5)/4+3^*21)$	3174804	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3-21)$
2914814	$98^7*(-6+5^4/3)^*21$	3174912	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3*(2+1))$
2918663	$-9^*(8^*(7-6^{\wedge}5)-4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$	3174966	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3-2-1)$
2918665	$-9^*(8^*(7-6^{\wedge}5)-4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$	3174972	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3)-21$
2919671	$9^*(8^*(7+6^{\wedge}5)+4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$	3174984	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3-2+1)$
2919673	$9^*(8^*(7+6^{\wedge}5)+4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$	3175014	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3)+21$
2934836	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$	3175020	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3+2+1)$
2934838	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$	3175056	$9^*(8+(7^6-5^4-3)^*(2+1))$
2934980	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$	3175116	$9^*(8+(7^6-5^4)^3)-21$
2934982	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$	3175158	$9^*(8+(7^6-5^4)^3)+21$
2939223	$-98+7^*((6^5/4/3)^2-1)$	3175164	$9^*(8+(7^6-5^4)^3+2+1)$
2939249	$-9^8+7^*((6^5/4/3)^2-1)$	3175182	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3+21)$
2939263	$-9^8+7^*((6^5/4/3)^2+1)$	3175218	$9^*(8+(7^6-5^4+3)^*(2+1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
3175326	$9*(8+(7^6-54)*3+21)$	3319635	$(9+876)*(5^4*3^2+1)$
3175425	$9*(-8+(7^6+5-43)*(2+1))$	3320103	$9*(8^7/6+5^4*(32-1))$
3175569	$9*(8+(7^6+5-43)*(2+1))$	3325719	$9*(8^7/6+5^4*32-1)$
3175965	$9*(-8+(7^6-54/3)*(2+1))$	3325737	$9*(8^7/6+5^4*32+1)$
3176019	$9*(-8+(7^6-5-4)*3-21)$	3325751	$-9*(8*7^6-5*4^3*2)-1$
3176109	$9*(8+(7^6-54/3)*(2+1))$	3325753	$-9*(8*7^6-5*4^3*2)+1$
3176416	$-98+(7^6*(5+4)-3)*(2+1)$	3331353	$9*(8^7/6+5^4*(32+1))$
3176482	$9*((-8+7^6*(5+4))/3-2)+1$	3333360	$(9+8)*((7^6*5+4)/3-2-1)$
3176630	$98+(7^6*(5+4)+3)*(2+1)$	3333462	$(9+8)*((7^6*5+4)/3+2+1)$
3176937	$9*(-8+(7^6+54/3)*(2+1))$	3346353	$9*8^7/6+5^4*321$
3177081	$9*(8+(7^6+54/3)*(2+1))$	3407748	$-9*8-(7+6)*(5-4^3*2-1)$
3177161	$98+(7^6+5^4)*3^2(2+1)$	3407996	$9*8+(7+6)*(5+4^3*2-1)$
3177477	$9*(-8+(7^6-5+43)*(2+1))$	3408022	$9*8+(7+6)*(5+4^3*2+1)$
3177621	$9*(8+(7^6-5+43)*(2+1))$	3414474	$(9+87*(6-5^4*3))*-21$
3177828	$9*(-8+(7^6+54-3)*(2+1))$	3414852	$(9-87*(6-5^4*3))*21$
3177864	$9*(8+(7^6+54)*3-21)$	3436776	$(9+87*(6+5^4*3))*21$
3177882	$9*(-8+(7^6+54)*3-2-1)$	3450512	$(9-(8-7)/6)*(5^4*(3/2)-1)$
3177888	$9*(8+(7^6+54)*3)-21$	3466788	$(9-8^7*(-7+6))*(5^4*(3/2)-1)$
3177918	$9*(-8+(7^6+54)*3+2-1)$	3472244	$9^8(8-7+6)-5*(4^3*2+1)$
3177990	$9*(-8+(7^6+54+3)*(2+1))$	3472254	$9^8(8-7+6)-5*(4^3*2-1)$
3178032	$9*(8+(7^6+54)*3)-21$	3478977	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4^3)/21)$
3178074	$9*(8+(7^6+54)*3)+21$	3479121	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4^3)/21)$
3178080	$9*(8+(7^6+54)*3+2+1)$	3484656	$(98+7^6*(5^4-3))/21$
3178242	$9*(8+(7^6+54)*3+21)$	3500103	$9*(8^7/6+5^4*3^2*21)$
3180825	$9*(-8+(7^6+54*3)*(2+1))$	3507732	$9*(-876+5^4*(3/2)-1)$
3180969	$9*(8+(7^6+54*3)*(2+1))$	3507750	$9*(-876+5^4*(3/2)+1)$
3182256	$9*(-8+(7^6+5*43)*(2+1))$	3514779	$9*(-87-6+5^4*(3/2)-1)$
3182400	$9*(8+(7^6+5*43)*(2+1))$	3514797	$9*(-87-6+5^4*(3/2)+1)$
3191112	$9*(-8+(7^6+543)*(2+1))$	3514860	$9*(-8-76+5^4*(3/2)-1)$
3191256	$9*(8+(7^6+543)*(2+1))$	3514878	$9*(-8-76+5^4*(3/2)+1)$
3193137	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)*3-21)$	3514887	$9*(-87+6+5^4*(3/2)-1)$
3193281	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3-21)$	3514905	$9*(-87+6+5^4*(3/2)+1)$
3193515	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)*3+21)$	3516228	$9*(-8+76+5^4*(3/2)-1)$
3193659	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3+21)$	3516246	$9*(-8+76+5^4*(3/2)+1)$
3202689	$-98*(7^6*5+4)/(3-21)$	3516372	$9*(8+76+5^4*(3/2)-1)$
3246978	$9*(8^7/6-5^4*(3-21))$	3516390	$9*(8+76+5^4*(3/2)+1)$
3250383	$(-9+876)*(5^4*3^2-1)$	3516453	$9*(87+6+5^4*(3/2)-1)$
3252117	$(-9+876)*(5^4*3^2+1)$	3516471	$9*(87+6+5^4*(3/2)+1)$
3255168	$-9+(8+7^6)*(5^4/3+21)$	3518270	$(98+7^6*(5^4+3))/21$
3257667	$(98+7^6)*(5^4/3+21)$	3520314	$9*(87*6+5^4*(3/2)-1)$
3263286	$9*(8^7/6+(5^4-3)*21)$	3520332	$9*(87*6+5^4*(3/2)+1)$
3264420	$9*(8^7/6+(5^4+3)*21)$	3521088	$9*(8*7^6+5^4*(3/2)-1)$
3275232	$(9-8/(7+6))*(5^4*(3/2)-1)$	3521106	$9*(8*7^6+5^4*(3/2)+1)$
3277116	$9*876*(5^4/3^2-1)$	3523518	$9*(876+5^4*(3/2)+1)$
3289636	$9*8*(7^6/54-3)*21$	3523859	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4*(4+3))*2)-1$
3291974	$(-98+(7^6-5)*4/3)*21$	3523861	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4*(4+3))*2)+1$
3292254	$(-98+(7^6+5)*4/3)*21$	3524003	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4*(4+3))*2)-1$
3292651	$-9+8*(7^6-54)*(3+2^2-1)$	3524005	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4*(4+3))*2)+1$
3292669	$9+8*(7^6-54)*(3+2^2-1)$	3524283	$9*87*(6+5^4/3)*21$
3292884	$9*876*(5^4/3^2+1)$	3526767	$9*((8*7^6-54/3)/2-1)$
3293605	$9*(8*7^6/54-3)*21$	3527118	$(-98+7^6*5/4)*(3+21)$
3293855	$-9-(8-(7^6-5)*4/3)*21$	3529269	$-9-(8-7^6*5/4)*(3+21)$
3293873	$9-(8-(7^6-5)*4/3)*21$	3529287	$9-(8-7^6*5/4)*(3+21)$
3293933	$-98-(7^6-5)*(4-32)-1$	3529375	$9*8+(7^6*5-4)*3^2+1$
3293935	$-98-(7^6-5)*(4-32)+1$	3529565	$9*8+(7^6*5+4)*3^2-1$
3293992	$9+(8*7^6-54)*(3+2^2-1)$	3529653	$-9+(8+7^6*5/4)*(3+21)$
3294129	$98-(7^6-5)*(4-32)-1$	3529671	$9+(8+7^6*5/4)*(3+21)$
3294352	$-9+(8*7^6+54)*(3+2^2-1)$	3531822	$(98+7^6*5/4)*(3+21)$
3294370	$9+(8*7^6+54)*(3+2^2-1)$	3564444	$(9+8^7*(-7+6))*(5^4*(3/2)-1)$
3294409	$98-(7^6+5)*(4-32)-1$	3565181	$9-(8-76)/5*(4^3*2+1)$
3294411	$98-(7^6+5)*(4-32)+1$	3580720	$(9+(8-7)/6)*(5^4*(3/2)-1)$
3294489	$9+(8+(7^6+5)*4/3)*21$	3582579	$(98-7)*(-6+5^4*3^2*21)$
3295675	$-9+8*(7^6+54)*(3+2^2-1)$	3583671	$(98-7)*(6+5^4*3^2*21)$
3295693	$9+8*(7^6+54)*(3+2^2-1)$	3627646	$-98+(7^6-5^4)*(32-1)$
3296090	$98+(7^6-5)*4/3)*21$	3627842	$98+(7^6-5^4)*(32-1)$
3296370	$(98+(7^6+5)*4/3)*21$	3645428	$-9-8+(7^6-5^4)*(32-1)$
3298708	$9*8*(7^6/54+3)*21$	3645444	$-9+8+(7^6-5^4)*(32-1)$
3306226	$-98*(7-6*(5^4*3^2-1))$	3645446	$9-8+(7^6-5^4)*(32-1)$
3307491	$-9+(8+7^6)*5^4*3^2*21$	3645462	$9+8+(7^6-5^4)*(32-1)$
3307509	$9+(8+7^6)*5^4*3^2*21$	3646401	$-98+(7^6-5^4)*(32-1)$
3307598	$98*(7+6*(5^4*3^2-1))$	3646597	$98+(7^6-5^4)*(32-1)$
3317865	$(9+876)*(5^4*3^2-1)$	3646742	$-98+(7^6-5^4)*(32-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
3646866	$-98+(7^6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	3779272	$9*(8+7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
3646892	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	3779639	$9*(8*7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
3646938	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*(32-1)$	3779641	$9*(8*7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
3646990	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*(32-1)$	3780576	$(9+87)*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
3647036	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	3797118	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5^{\wedge}(4*3/2)+1)$
3647062	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	3801010	$9-87/6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
3647176	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	3801039	$9-87/6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
3647186	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*(32-1)$	3801155	$9+87/6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
3647202	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	3801184	$9+87/6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
3647248	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*(32-1)$	3804858	$9*87*((6+5)^{\wedge}4/3-21)$
3647300	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*(32-1)$	3820726	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/3-21)$
3647346	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	3822490	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/3-2-1)$
3647372	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	3822735	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
3647496	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*(32-1)$	3822833	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
3647641	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)*(32-1)$	3823078	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/3+2+1)$
3647837	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)*(32-1)$	3824842	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/3+21)$
3648776	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(32-1)$	3841110	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)/3-21)$
3648792	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(32-1)$	3841796	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5*4)/3-21)$
3648794	$9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(32-1)$	3843119	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
3648810	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(32-1)$	3843217	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
3661686	$(-9+(87+6)*5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	3843805	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5*4)/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
3661866	$-9+(87+6)*5^{\wedge}4*3*21$	3843903	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5*4)/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
3661884	$9+(87+6)*5^{\wedge}4*3*21$	3844148	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5*4)/3+2+1)$
3662064	$(9+(87+6)*5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	3845226	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)/3+21)$
3666396	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(32-1)$	3845912	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5*4)/3+21)$
3666592	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(32-1)$	3856349	$98*(-7/6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
3669092	$-98/7*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	3857476	$98*(-7-6+5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
3669105	$-98/7*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	3860024	$98*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
3669107	$-98/7*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	3861151	$98*(7/6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
3670912	$98/7*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	3861694	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(32+1)$
3670925	$98/7*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	3861890	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(32+1)$
3670927	$98/7*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	3880618	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(32+1)$
3670940	$98/7*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	3880634	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(32+1)$
3674314	$-98*(7-6*5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$	3880636	$9-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(32+1)$
3675686	$98*(7+6*5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$	3880652	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(32+1)$
3698499	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*43)*21$	3881659	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)*(32+1)$
3728049	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3)*2-1)$	3882022	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*(32+1)$
3728083	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3)*2+1)$	3882218	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*(32+1)$
3729303	$9*(87*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	3882286	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*(32+1)$
3729321	$9*(87*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	3882300	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)-21)$
3756000	$(9+8/(7+6))*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	3882326	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)-2)-1$
3762031	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4-321)$	3882328	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)-2)+1$
3762049	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4-321)$	3882352	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*(32+1)$
3762351	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4-321)$	3882362	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)+2)-1$
3762369	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4-321)$	3882364	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)+2)+1$
3763031	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3+2-1)$	3882470	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)-2)-1$
3763049	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3+2-1)$	3882472	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)-2)+1$
3764113	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4-3*21)$	3882482	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*(32+1)$
3764278	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4-321$	3882506	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)+2)-1$
3764296	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4-321$	3882508	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)+2)+1$
3764353	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4-32-1)$	3882534	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)+21)$
3764369	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4-32+1)$	3882548	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*(32+1)$
3764425	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4-3-21)$	3882616	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*(32+1)$
3764433	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4-3*21)$	3882812	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*(32+1)$
3764473	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4+3-21)$	3883175	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)*(32+1)$
3765111	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4+3+21)$	3884182	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(32+1)$
3765121	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4+3*21)$	3884198	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(32+1)$
3765183	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4+32+1)$	3884200	$9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(32+1)$
3765185	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4+32-1)$	3884216	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(32+1)$
3765201	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4+32+1)$	3887757	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$
3765240	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4+321$	3888243	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*((5*4)^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
3765258	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4+321$	3902944	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(32+1)$
3766505	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(3+2-1)$	3903140	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(32+1)$
3767167	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4+321)$	3929271	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)/4-321)$
3767185	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4+321)$	3931179	$9-(8+7)*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
3778344	$9*(-87+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	3933129	$9+(8+7)*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
3778362	$9*(-87+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	3933159	$9+(8+7)*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
3778631	$9*(-8*7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	3935049	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)/4+321)$
3778633	$9*(-8*7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	3936299	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*2-1)$
3779000	$9*(-8-7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	3936333	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*2+1)$
3779002	$9*(-8-7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	3978697	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$
3779270	$9*(8+7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	3978731	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
3978901	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5^4 + 3) * 2 - 1)$	4215807	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 543) / 2 - 1)$
3978935	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5^4 + 3) * 2 + 1)$	4215888	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 - 543) / 2 + 1)$
3980097	$9^8 * ((8+7) / 6) * (-5 + 4^4 * (3^2 + 1))$	4227615	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5^4 * 3) / 2 - 1)$
3981587	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 543) * 2 - 1)$	4227633	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5^4 * 3) / 2 + 1)$
3981621	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 543) * 2 + 1)$	4229523	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 54^3) / 2 - 1)$
3989169	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5^4 * 4^3) * 2 - 1)$	4229541	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 54^3) / 2 + 1)$
3989203	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5^4 * 4^3) * 2 + 1)$	4232223	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 - 5) * 4 - 321)$
3997703	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5 - 4^3) * 2 - 1)$	4233303	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 54 - 3) / 2 - 1)$
3997737	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5 - 4^3) * 2 + 1)$	4233321	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 54 - 3) / 2 + 1)$
3998009	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5^4 * 3) * 2 - 1)$	4233348	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 - 54) * (3 + 2 - 1))$
3998043	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5 - 4^3) * 2 - 1)$	4233492	$9 * (8 + (7^6 - 54) * (3 + 2 - 1))$
3998077	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5 - 4^3) * 2 + 1)$	4233519	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 54 + 3) / 2 - 1)$
3998859	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5 * (4 + 3)) * 2 - 1)$	4233537	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 54 + 3) / 2 + 1)$
3998893	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5 * (4 + 3)) * 2 + 1)$	4233627	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5 - 43) / 2 - 1)$
3999131	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - (5 + 4) * 3) * 2 - 1)$	4233645	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5 - 43) / 2 + 1)$
3999165	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - (5 + 4) * 3) * 2 + 1)$	4233987	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5 - 43) / 2 - 1)$
3999267	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5^4 * 3) * 2 - 1)$	4234005	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5 - 43) / 2 + 1)$
3999301	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5^4 * 3) * 2 + 1)$	4234707	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 54 / 3) / 2 - 1)$
3999505	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5 - 4^3) * 2 + 1)$	4234791	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 - 5) * 4 - 321)$
3999641	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5 - 4^3) * 2 - 1)$	4235273	$9 * (-8 + 7^6 * (5 - 4 + 3) - 2) - 1$
3999675	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5 - 4^3) * 2 + 1)$	4235275	$9 * (-8 + 7^6 * (5 - 4 + 3) - 2) + 1$
3999845	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5 - 4 + 3) * 2 - 1)$	4235453	$9 * (8 + 7^6 * (5 - 4 + 3) + 2) - 1$
3999907	$9 + 8 * (7^6 * (5 / 4 + 3) - 21)$	4235455	$9 * (8 + 7^6 * (5 - 4 + 3) + 2) + 1$
4000243	$9 + 8 * (7^6 * (5 / 4 + 3) + 21)$	4235937	$9 * (8 + (7^6 + 5) * 4 + 321)$
4000287	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5 + 4 - 3) * 2 + 1)$	4236021	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 54 / 3) / 2 + 1)$
4000457	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5 + 4 + 3) * 2 - 1)$	4236723	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5 + 43) / 2 - 1)$
4000491	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5 + 4 + 3) * 2 + 1)$	4236741	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5 + 43) / 2 + 1)$
4000627	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5 + 4^3) * 2 - 1)$	4237083	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5 + 43) / 2 - 1)$
4000831	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4 * 3) * 2 - 1)$	4237101	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5 + 43) / 2 + 1)$
4000865	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4 * 3) * 2 + 1)$	4237191	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 54 - 3) / 2 - 1)$
4000967	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + (5 + 4) * 3) * 2 - 1)$	4237209	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 54 - 3) / 2 + 1)$
4001001	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + (5 + 4) * 3) * 2 + 1)$	4237236	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 + 54) * (3 + 2 - 1))$
4001239	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5 * (4 + 3)) * 2 - 1)$	4237380	$9 * (8 + (7^6 + 54) * (3 + 2 - 1))$
4001273	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5 * (4 + 3)) * 2 + 1)$	4237407	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 54 + 3) / 2 - 1)$
4002055	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5 + 4^3) * 2 - 1)$	4237425	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 54 + 3) / 2 + 1)$
4002089	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5 + 4^3) * 2 + 1)$	4238001	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 - 5) * 4 + 321)$
4002395	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5 + 4^3) * 2 - 1)$	4238505	$9 * (8 + (7^6 + 5) * 4 + 321)$
4002429	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5 + 4^3) * 2 + 1)$	4241187	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 54^3) / 2 - 1)$
4010929	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4 * 3) * 2 - 1)$	4241205	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 54^3) / 2 + 1)$
4010963	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4 * 3) * 2 + 1)$	4243095	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5^4 * 3) / 2 - 1)$
4016233	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5^4 * 3^2 - 1)$	4243113	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5^4 * 3) / 2 + 1)$
4016267	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5^4 * 3^2 + 1)$	4245557	$9 * (-8 + 7^6 * 5) - 4^4 * (3^2 + 1)$
4018511	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 543) * 2 - 1)$	4245701	$9 * (8 + 7^6 * 5) - 4^4 * (3^2 + 1)$
4018545	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 543) * 2 + 1)$	4250442	$(9+8) * ((7 / (6 / 54)) ^ 3 - 21)$
4021197	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4 - 3) * 2 - 1)$	4250778	$(9+8) * ((7 / (6 / 54)) ^ 3 - 21)$
4021231	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4 - 3) * 2 + 1)$	4250820	$(9+8) * ((7 / (6 / 54)) ^ 3 + 21)$
4021401	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4 + 3) * 2 - 1)$	4251156	$(9+8) * ((7 / (6 / 54)) ^ 3 + 21)$
4021435	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4 + 3) * 2 + 1)$	4254840	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 + 543) / 2 - 1)$
4063799	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4 * 3) * 2 - 1)$	4254903	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 543) / 2 - 1)$
4063833	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4 * 3) * 2 + 1)$	4254921	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 543) / 2 + 1)$
4069895	$-9 + 8 * (7^6 * 5 - 43^2 + 1)$	4254984	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 + 543) / 2 + 1)$
4069913	$9 + 8 * (7^6 * 5 - 43^2 + 1)$	4272049	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + (5^4) ^ 3) * 2 - 1)$
4095009	$9 + 8 * (7 + 6) / 5^4 - 4^3 * 21$	4272083	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + (5^4) ^ 3) * 2 + 1)$
4104902	$9^8 - 7^6 * (5 * (4^3 + 2) + 1)$	4281081	$98 * (-7 + (6 / (5 + 4^3 * 2)) ^ 4 - 1)$
4115629	$(-98 + (7^6 * 5 - 4) / 3) * 21$	4282453	$98 * (7 + (6 / (5 + 4^3 * 2)) ^ 4 - 1)$
4115685	$(-98 + (7^6 * 5 + 4) / 3) * 21$	4335000	$(-9 + 876) * 5^4 * (3^2 - 1)$
4117528	$9 - (8 - (7^6 * 5 - 4) / 3) * 21$	4340200	$9^8 - 7^6 * (5 * (4^3 + 2) - 1)$
4117566	$9 - (8 - (7^6 * 5 + 4) / 3) * 21$	4404045	$9 + (8 + 76) / 5 * (4^3 + 2 + 1)$
4117584	$9 - (8 - (7^6 * 5 + 4) / 3) * 21$	4409505	$9 + 8 * (7^6 / 5^4 - 4 - 3) * 21$
4117841	$98 + (7^6 * 5 + 4) / 3^2 * 21$	4410072	$9 + (8 * 7^6 / 5^4 - 4 + 3) * 21$
4117864	$9 + (8 + (7^6 * 5 - 4) / 3) * 21$	4413537	$9 + 8 * 7^6 * (6 / 5^4 - 4 + 3) * 21$
4117902	$-9 + (8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4) / 3) * 21$	4425000	$(9 + 876) * 5^4 * (3^2 - 1)$
4117920	$9 + (8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4) / 3) * 21$	4443426	$(-9 - 8) * (765 - 4^3 * 2 + 1)$
4119745	$(98 + (7^6 * 5 - 4) / 3) * 21$	4443460	$(-9 - 8) * (765 - 4^3 * 2 - 1)$
4119801	$(98 + (7^6 * 5 + 4) / 3) * 21$	4452861	$(-9 - 8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4^3 * 2 + 1)$
4133745	$(98 + 7) * (-6 + 5^4 * 3 * 21)$	4452895	$(-9 - 8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4^3 * 2 - 1)$
4135005	$(98 + 7) * (6 + 5^4 * 3 * 21)$	4453100	$-9 - (87 / (6 - (5 + 4) ^ 3 * 2)) ^ 4 - 1$
4141891	$9 - (8 - 7^6) / 5 * (4^3 * 2 + 1)$	4453118	$9 - (87 / (6 - (5 + 4) ^ 3 * 2)) ^ 4 - 1$
4159674	$9^8 - (8 + 7 + 6) * (5^4 / 3^2 + 1)$	4455156	$(-9 - 8) * (7^6 + 6 + 5) - 4^3 * 2 - 1$
4183096	$(9 - 8 * (7^6 * 5 + 4)) * (3^4 - 2 - 1)$	4455666	$(-9 - 8) * (7^6 + 5 - 4^3 * 2 - 1)$
4193992	$9 + 8^8 * (7 + 6 - 5) / 4 - 321$	4456414	$(9 + 8) * ((-7 + 6) ^ 5 + 4^3 * 2 - 1)$
4194616	$-9 + 8^8 * (7 + 6 - 5) / 4 + 321$	4457230	$(9 + 8) * (7^6 + 5 + 4^3 * 2 - 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
4457264	$(9+8)*(7*6+5+4^3*2+1)$	4708569	$9+8*(7^6*5+4+321)$
4457536	$(9+8)*((7+6)*5+4^3*2-1)$	4709399	$-9+8*(7^6*5+432-1)$
4457570	$(9+8)*((7+6)*5+4^3*2+1)$	4709415	$-9+8*(7^6*5+432+1)$
4457740	$(9+8)*(7*(6+5)+4^3*2-1)$	4709417	$9+8*(7^6*5+432-1)$
4457774	$(9+8)*(7*(6+5)+4^3*2+1)$	4709433	$9+8*(7^6*5+432+1)$
4460001	$(9+8)*(7*6*5+4^3*2-1)$	4713175	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4^3*21)$
4460035	$(9+8)*(7*6*5+4^3*2+1)$	4713193	$9+8*(7^6*5+4^3*21)$
4469436	$(9+8)*(765+4^3*2-1)$	4716223	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4^3*21)$
4469470	$(9+8)*(765+4^3*2+1)$	4716241	$9+8*(7^6*5+4^3*21)$
4492176	$(9+(8+7)/6)*(5^4*(3/2)-1)$	4716703	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4^3*21)$
4492199	$(9+(8+7)/6)*(5^4*(3/2)+1)$	4716721	$9+8*(7^6*5+4^3*21)$
4499866	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)/4*3^2-1)$	4716751	$(9/(8^7+(6+5-4)^3))^{\wedge-1}$
4499900	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)/4*3^2+1)$	4717827	$9*((8^7(7-6+5)-43)^2+1)$
4640575	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*(3/2)-1)$	4718708	$98+(7+6+5)*(4^3*2+1)$
4640609	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*(3/2)+1)$	4720735	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4^3*2-1)$
4691151	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*2-1)$	4720751	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4^3*2+1)$
4691167	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*2+1)$	4720753	$9+8*(7^6*5+4^3*2-1)$
4691169	$9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*2-1)$	4720769	$9+8*(7^6*5+4^3*2+1)$
4691185	$9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*2+1)$	4764698	$9*(-8+(7^6*(5+4)-3)/2)-1$
4695199	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*21)$	4764700	$9*(-8+(7^6*(5+4)-3)/2)+1$
4695217	$9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*21)$	4764725	$9*(-8+(7^6*(5+4)+3)/2)-1$
4695679	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*21)$	4764727	$9*(-8+(7^6*(5+4)+3)/2)+1$
4695697	$9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*21)$	4764842	$9*(8+(7^6*(5+4)-3)/2)-1$
4698727	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*21)$	4764844	$9*(8+(7^6*(5+4)-3)/2)+1$
4698745	$9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*21)$	4764869	$9*(8+(7^6*(5+4)+3)/2)-1$
4702487	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*2-1)$	4764871	$9*(8+(7^6*(5+4)+3)/2)+1$
4702503	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*2+1)$	4776719	$9^8(8-7+6)-5^4*(3^2+1)$
4702505	$9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*2-1)$	4777969	$9^8(8-7+6)-5^4*(3^2-1)$
4702521	$9+8*(7^6*5-4^3*2+1)$	4780469	$9^8(8-7+6)-5^4*(3+2-1)$
4703351	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4-321)$	4781085	$9^8(8-7+6)-(5^4+3)^*(2+1)$
4703369	$9+8*(7^6*5-4-321)$	4781103	$9^8(8-7+6)-(5^4-3)^*(2+1)$
4703415	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4-321)$	4784835	$9^8(8-7+6)+(5^4-3)^*(2+1)$
4703433	$9+8*(7^6*5+4-321)$	4784853	$9^8(8-7+6)+(5^4+3)^*(2+1)$
4703783	$-9+8*((7^6-54)^*(3+2)-1)$	4785469	$9^8(8-7+6)+5^4*(3+2-1)$
4703799	$-9+8*((7^6-54)^*(3+2)+1)$	4787969	$9^8(8-7+6)+5^4*(3^2-1)$
4703801	$9+8*((7^6-54)^*(3+2)-1)$	4789219	$9^8(8-7+6)+5^4*(3^2+1)$
4703817	$9+8*((7^6-54)^*(3+2)+1)$	4806065	$(9+8*7/6)/(5+4^3*2)^{\wedge-1}$
4704775	$-9+8*(7^6*5-(4+3)*21)$	4823305	$-98+(7^6-5)^*(43-2)-1$
4704793	$9+8*(7^6*5-(4+3)*21)$	4823307	$-98+(7^6-5)^*(43-2)+1$
4704895	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4*(32+1))$	4823501	$98+(7^6-5)^*(43-2)-1$
4704913	$9+8*(7^6*5-4*(32+1))$	4823503	$98+(7^6-5)^*(43-2)+1$
4704959	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4*(32-1))$	4823715	$-98+(7^6+5)^*(43-2)-1$
4704977	$9+8*(7^6*5-4*(32-1))$	4823717	$-98+(7^6+5)^*(43-2)+1$
4705201	$9+8*(7^6*5-4*(3+21))$	4823911	$98+(7^6+5)^*(43-2)-1$
4705375	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4*(3-21))$	4823913	$98+(7^6+5)^*(43-2)+1$
4705393	$9+8*(7^6*5+4*(3-21))$	4875906	$9+(87+6)/5*(4^3*2+1)$
4705479	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4-3*21)$	4876008	$(-9+876)*(5^4*3^2-1)$
4705497	$9+8*(7^6*5+4-3*21)$	4877742	$(-9+876)*(5^4*3^2+1)$
4705586	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4^3)-21$	4940553	$9+8*((7^6-5)/4-3)*21$
4705611	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4^3+2^2-1)$	4940950	$-98+(7^6-5)^*(43-2+1)$
4705621	$9+8*(7^6*5-4^3+2^2-1)$	4940973	$9+8*((7^6+5)/4-3)*21$
4705633	$9+8*(7^6*5-4^3+2-1)$	4940994	$9+(8*(7^6-5)/4-3)*21$
4706299	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4^3+2^2-1)$	4941099	$9-(8+7^6*(5-4-3))*21$
4706309	$9+8*(7^6*5+4^3+2^2-1)$	4941146	$98+(7^6-5)^*(43-2+1)$
4706317	$9+8*(7^6*5+4^3+2^2-1)$	4941231	$(-9-8*7^6*(5/4-3))^*(2+1)$
4706334	$9+8*(7^6*5+4^3)+21$	4941244	$98*(7^6*(5+4)-3)/21$
4706441	$9+8*(7^6*5+4^3*21)$	4941272	$98*(7^6*(5+4)+3)/21$
4706527	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4*(3-21))$	4941285	$(9-8*7^6*(5/4-3))^*(2+1)$
4706545	$9+8*(7^6*5-4*(3-21))$	4941370	$-98+(7^6+5)^*(43-2+1)$
4706719	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4*(3+21))$	4941414	$9+(8*(7^6+5)/4-3)*21$
4706943	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4*(32-1))$	4941435	$9+(8-7^6*(5-4-3))^*21$
4706961	$9+8*(7^6*5+4*(32-1))$	4941543	$-9+8*((7^6-5)/4+3)*21$
4707007	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4*(32+1))$	4941561	$9+8*((7^6-5)/4+3)*21$
4707025	$9+8*(7^6*5+4*(32+1))$	4941566	$98+(7^6+5)^*(43-2+1)$
4707127	$-9+8*(7^6*5+(4+3)*21)$	4941981	$9+8*((7^6+5)/4+3)*21$
4707145	$9+8*(7^6*5+(4+3)*21)$	4943943	$9*((8*7^6+5^4*3)/2-1)$
4708119	$-9+8*((7^6+54)^*(3+2)+1)$	4943961	$9*((8*7^6+5^4*3)/2+1)$
4708121	$9+8*((7^6+54)^*(3+2)-1)$	4976397	$9^8((8+7)/6)^*(5*(4^3)^2-1)$
4708137	$9+8*((7^6+54)^*(3+2)+1)$	4976883	$9^8((8+7)/6)^*(5*(4^3)^2+1)$
4708487	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4+321)$	4977240	$(9+876)*(5^4*3^2-1)$
4708505	$9+8*(7^6*5-4+321)$	4979010	$(9+876)*(5^4*3^2+1)$
4708551	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4+321)$	4999772	$-98+(7^6-5)^*(43-2^2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
5000057	$(9+8)*((7^6*5-4+3)/2-1)$	5293350	$9*(-8+7^6*5-43*2-1)$
5000159	$(9+8)*((7^6*5+4+3)/2+1)$	5293374	$9*(8+7^6*5)-43*21$
5000197	$-98+(7^6+5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	5293725	$9*(-8+7^6*5-43)-21$
5000393	$98+(7^6+5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	5293767	$9*(-8+7^6*5-43)+21$
5037839	$-9*(8*7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*2-1$	5293920	$9*(8+7^6*5-4)-321$
5037841	$-9*(8*7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*2+1$	5294021	$9*(8+7^6*5)-4^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
5078014	$-98+(7+6)*(5^4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	5294076	$9*(8+7^6*5-4/3-21)$
5078040	$-9*8+(7+6)*(5^4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	5294077	$98+(7^6-5)*(43+2)-1$
5078066	$-9*8+(7+6)*(5^4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	5294333	$-98+(7^6+5)*(43+2)+1$
5078184	$9*8+(7+6)*(5^4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	5294334	$9*(-8+7^6*5+4*(3+21))$
5078210	$9*8+(7+6)*(5^4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	5294389	$9*(-8+7^6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
5078236	$98+(7+6)*(5^4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	5294490	$9*(-8+7^6*5+4)+321$
5117416	$-98+(7^6-5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	5294643	$9*(8+7^6*5+43)-21$
5117612	$98+(7^6-5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	5294685	$9*(8+7^6*5+43)+21$
5117851	$-98+(7^6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	5294916	$9*(-8+7^6*5+43*2+1)$
5118047	$98+(7^6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	5295036	$9*(-8+7^6*5)+43*21$
5176238	$-98+(7^6-5)*(43+2-1)$	5295180	$9*(8+7^6*5)+43*21$
5176434	$98+(7^6-5)*(43+2-1)$	5295321	$9*(-8+7^6*5+4*(32+1))$
5176678	$-98+(7^6+5)*(43+2-1)$	5295417	$9*(-8+7^6*5)+4*321$
5176874	$98+(7^6+5)*(43+2-1)$	5295561	$9*(8+7^6*5)+4*321$
5226905	$9*(-8+7^6*5-4/3/21))$	5295572	$9*(8+7^6*5+(4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
5228597	$9*(-8+7^6*5)-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	5295574	$9*(8+7^6*5+(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
5228741	$9*(8+7^6*5)-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	5296554	$9*(-8+(7^6+54)*(3+2)-1)$
5228870	$(-9+8*(7^6*5+4))*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	5296572	$9*(-8+(7^6+54)*(3+2)+1)$
5235678	$9^8*76/(5^4-3/21)$	5296716	$9*(8+(7^6+54)*(3+2)+1)$
5243072	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)+4^{\wedge}3)/(2+1)$	5297058	$9*(-8+7^6*5+4+321)$
5249475	$(-9*8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	5297130	$9*(8+7^6*5-4+321)$
5250630	$(-9-8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	5297202	$9*(8+7^6*5+4+321)$
5250810	$-9-(8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	5298012	$9*(-8+7^6*5+432-1)$
5250828	$9-(8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	5298030	$9*(-8+7^6*5+432+1)$
5250915	$-9*8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3*21$	5298156	$9*(8+7^6*5+432-1)$
5251059	$9*8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3*21$	5298174	$9*(8+7^6*5+432+1)$
5251146	$-9+(8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	5302260	$9*(-8+7^6*5+43*21)$
5251164	$9+(8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	5302404	$9*(8+7^6*5+43*21)$
5251344	$(9+8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	5305689	$9*(-8+7^6*5+4*321)$
5252499	$(9*8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	5305833	$9*(8+7^6*5+4*321)$
5256375	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*4)*321$	5306373	$9*(8+7^6*5+4^{\wedge}3*21)$
5257268	$9*(-8+7^6*5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	5310517	$9*(-8+7^6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
5257270	$9*(-8+7^6*5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	5310661	$9*(8+7^6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
5257412	$9*(8+7^6*5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	5310765	$9*(-8+7^6*5+43^{\wedge}2-1)$
5257414	$9*(8+7^6*5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	5310783	$9*(-8+7^6*5+43^{\wedge}2+1)$
5274972	$9^8-(7^6+5*4)*321$	5310909	$9*(8+7^6*5+43^{\wedge}2-1)$
5277483	$9*(-8+7^6*5-43^{\wedge}2-1)$	5310927	$9*(8+7^6*5+43^{\wedge}2+1)$
5277501	$9*(-8+7^6*5-43^{\wedge}2+1)$	5330996	$9*(-8+7^6*5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
5277627	$9*(8+7^6*5-43^{\wedge}2-1)$	5330998	$9*(-8+7^6*5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
5277645	$9*(8+7^6*5-43^{\wedge}2+1)$	5331140	$9*(8+7^6*5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
5277749	$9*(-8+7^6*5)-4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	5331142	$9*(8+7^6*5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
5277893	$9*(8+7^6*5)-4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	5333631	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*4/3*2-1)$
5282037	$9*(-8+7^6*5-4^{\wedge}3*21)$	5333665	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*4/3*2+1)$
5282181	$9*(8+7^6*5-4^{\wedge}3*21)$	5342007	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4^{\wedge}3(2+1))$
5282577	$9*(-8+7^6*5-4*321)$	5342025	$9+8*(7^6*5+4^{\wedge}3(2+1))$
5282721	$9*(8+7^6*5-4*321)$	5359669	$9*(-8+7^6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
5286006	$9*(-8+7^6*5-43*21)$	5359813	$9*(8+7^6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
5286150	$9*(8+7^6*5-43*21)$	5361361	$9*(-8+7^6*5+(5+4/3/21))$
5287812	$9^8-(7^6-5*4)*321$	5361505	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4/3/21))$
5290254	$9*(-8+7^6*5-432+1)$	5372703	$98*((7^6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
5290380	$9*(8+7^6*5-432-1)$	5372899	$98*((7^6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$
5290398	$9*(8+7^6*5-432+1)$	5381775	$(9+8)*(7*6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
5291208	$9*(-8+7^6*5-4-321)$	5381809	$(9+8)*(7*6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
5291280	$9*(-8+7^6*5+4-321)$	5410658	$(9+8)*7^6+5^{\wedge}4*321$
5291352	$9*(8+7^6*5-4-321)$	5411526	$-98+(7^6-5)*(43+2+1)$
5291694	$9*(-8+(7^6-54)*(3+2)-1)$	5411722	$98+(7^6-5)*(43+2+1)$
5291838	$9*(8+(7^6-54)*(3+2)-1)$	5411986	$-98+(7^6+5)*(43+2+1)$
5291856	$9*(8+(7^6-54)*(3+2)+1)$	5412182	$98+(7^6+5)*(43+2+1)$
5292810	$9*(-8+7^6*5-(4+3)*21)$	5418750	$(-9+876)*5^4*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
5292836	$9*(-8+7^6*5-(4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	5428644	$(9+8)*(7^6*5/(4+3)+2)-1$
5292838	$9*(-8+7^6*5-(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	5428678	$(9+8)*(7^6*5/(4+3)+2)+1$
5292849	$9*(-8+7^6*5)-4*321$	5458208	$(9/8/(7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
5292993	$9*(8+7^6*5)-4*321$	5504781	$9+(8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)-4*3)*21$
5293017	$9*(-8+7^6*5-4*(32-1))$	5504970	$9+(8^{\wedge}(7-(6-5)^{\wedge}4)-3)*21$
5293089	$9*(8+7^6*5-4*(32+1))$	5505061	$9+(8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)+4/3)*21$
5293230	$9*(-8+7^6*5)-43*21$	5505096	$9+(8^{\wedge}(7-(6-5)^{\wedge}4)+3)*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
5505285	$9+(8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	5856774	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$
5516690	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	5881199	$9^{\wedge}87/(65^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1$
5526600	$9^{\wedge}(8+7)^{\wedge}((6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	5881201	$9^{\wedge}87/(65^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
5526870	$9^{\wedge}(8+7)^{\wedge}((6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	5882270	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3/2+1)$
5531250	$(9+876)^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	5882312	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
5543700	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	5882392	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
5543734	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	5882508	$98+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
5558040	$9^{\wedge}(-8+((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3)^{\wedge}21)$	5882588	$98+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
5559174	$9^{\wedge}(-8+((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3)^{\wedge}21)$	5882630	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3/2+1)$
5559318	$9^{\wedge}(8+((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3)^{\wedge}21)$	5968173	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
5617134	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)/2^{\wedge}-1$	5968207	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
5617170	$(9+8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)/2^{\wedge}-1$	5968241	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
5646993	$9+8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}(5+4-3)-21)$	5968275	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
5647311	$-9+8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}(5+4-3)+21)$	5974272	$9^{\wedge}8^{\wedge}(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}321)$
5647329	$9+8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}(5+4-3)+21)$	5987286	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
5664057	$9+87/6^{\wedge}(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	5996988	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-21)$
5664068	$-9+87/6^{\wedge}(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	5997039	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
5664086	$9+87/6^{\wedge}(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	5997702	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+21)$
5672828	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	5999062	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
5700860	$9^{\wedge}(-8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	5999096	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
5700862	$9^{\wedge}(-8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	5999130	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
5701004	$9^{\wedge}(8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	5999589	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
5701006	$9^{\wedge}(8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	5999623	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
5733931	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1)$	5999657	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
5734127	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1)$	5999827	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge}(4-3+2)-1)$
5734225	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$	5999861	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge}(4-3+2)+1)$
5734421	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1)$	5999883	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}(5^{\wedge}4-3))^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
5749023	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6000167	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
5749219	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	6000315	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}(5^{\wedge}4-3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
5751988	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	6000337	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge}(4-3+2)-1)$
5754168	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6000371	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge}(4-3+2)+1)$
5754364	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	6000541	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
5756765	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6000575	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
5756961	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	6000609	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
5761322	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6001068	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
5761812	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6001102	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
5761959	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	6001136	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
5762204	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$	6002496	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-21)$
5762351	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6003159	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
5762400	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1)$	6003210	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+21)$
5762547	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	6027792	$(9+8)^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
5762841	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6029217	$9^{\wedge}8-8-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
5763037	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	6029237	$-98-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
5763184	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$	6029263	$9^{\wedge}8-8-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
5764017	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)/2+1)$	6029361	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
5765585	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)/2-1)$	6029387	$98-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
5766026	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1)$	6029407	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
5766222	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$	6029433	$98-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
5766418	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2-1)$	6031923	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
5766565	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$	6031957	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
5766614	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2+1)$	6031991	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
5766761	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	6032025	$(9+8)^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
5767055	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6050709	$9^{\wedge}(8^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5/(4+3)+21)$
5767137	$-9+(87-65)^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	6081773	$9+(8+76/5)^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
5767199	$9+(87-65)^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	6093684	$9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)+5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
5767202	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1)$	6093694	$9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)+5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
5767251	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	6111071	$9^{\wedge}(8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
5767398	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6111073	$9^{\wedge}(8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
5767496	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6111791	$9^{\wedge}(8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6+5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
5767790	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	6111793	$9^{\wedge}(8^{\wedge}(7^{\wedge}6+5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
5768280	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	6142033	$9^{\wedge}8/7-(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/21$
5772641	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6147414	$(-9+87)^{\wedge}(6^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}21$
5772837	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	6149115	$9^{\wedge}8/(-7/((6^{\wedge}5/4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1))$
5775238	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6149463	$9^{\wedge}8/7+6^{\wedge}5/((4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
5775434	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	6149516	$9^{\wedge}8/7-(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3)/21$
5780383	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6149593	$9^{\wedge}8/7+6^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3/21$
5780579	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$	6156703	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
5795181	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1)$	6156899	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$
5795377	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1)$	6201600	$9^{\wedge}(8+7)^{\wedge}((6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
5795475	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$	6201870	$9^{\wedge}(8+7)^{\wedge}((6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
5795671	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1)$	6222584	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}((5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
5856578	$98^{\wedge}((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$	6336167	$-9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}(5^{\wedge}4-3/21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
6336222	$-9-8+7^6*(54-3/21)$	6902368	$(9/(8*(7^6+5)*(4^3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$
6336238	$-9+8+7^6*(54-3/21)$	6906357	$9*(876^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)-2-1)$
6336240	$9-8+7^6*(54-3/21)$	6906411	$9*(876^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)+2+1)$
6336256	$9+8+7^6*(54-3/21)$	6940898	$-98-(7^6-5)*(4-3*21)$
6336311	$9*8+7^6*(54-3/21)$	6941094	$98-(7^6-5)*(4-3*21)$
6342709	$9*(-8+7^6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	6941172	$-98-7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-21$
6342853	$9*(8+7^6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	6941214	$-98-7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+21$
6350049	$9*(-8+(7^6-54)*3^2-1)$	6941368	$98-7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-21$
6350067	$9*(-8+(7^6-54)*3^2+1)$	6941410	$98-7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+21$
6350265	$9*((8+(7^6-54)*3)^2-1)$	6941488	$-98-(7^6+5)*(4-3*21)$
6350283	$9*((8+(7^6-54)*3)^2+1)$	6941684	$98-(7^6+5)*(4-3*21)$
6351893	$9*(-8+(7^6-5*4)*3^2)-1$	6945562	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^6*543)/(-2-1)$
6351895	$9*(-8+(7^6-5*4)*3^2)+1$	6986224	$98*((7/(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}-2-1)$
6352037	$9*(8+(7^6-5*4)*3^2)-1$	6986420	$98*((7/(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}-2+1)$
6352039	$9*(8+(7^6-5*4)*3^2)+1$	6999801	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)*(4+3)/2-1)$
6352487	$9*(-8+(7^6-5-4)*3^2)-1$	6999835	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)*(4+3)/2+1)$
6352489	$9*(-8+(7^6-5-4)*3^2)+1$	7000073	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}(6+5-4)-3)/2-1)$
6352533	$(-9+8*(7^6-5)/4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	7000107	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}(6+5-4)-3)/2+1)$
6352752	$(-98+7^6*54/3)*(2+1)$	7000124	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}(6+5-4)+3)/2-1)$
6353340	$(98+7^6*54/3)*(2+1)$	7000158	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}(6+5-4)+3)/2+1)$
6353559	$(9+8*(7^6+5)/4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	7000396	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*(4+3)/2-1)$
6353603	$9*(8+(7^6+5+4)*3^2)-1$	7000430	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*(4+3)/2+1)$
6353605	$9*(8+(7^6+5+4)*3^2)+1$	7030719	$9*(8*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*32)-1)$
6354053	$9*(-8+(7^6+5*4)*3^2)-1$	7058679	$9*(-8+7^6*5^4/3-21)$
6354055	$9*(-8+(7^6+5*4)*3^2)+1$	7058775	$9*((8+7^6*5^4)/3-21)$
6354197	$9*(8+(7^6+5*4)*3^2)-1$	7059105	$9*((-8+7^6*5^4)/3+21)$
6354199	$9*(8+(7^6+5*4)*3^2)+1$	7059201	$9*(8+7^6*5^4/3+21)$
6355881	$9*(-8+(7^6+54)*3^2-1)$	7076224	$98*((7/(6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}-2-1)$
6355899	$9*(-8+(7^6+54)*3^2+1)$	7076420	$98*((7/(6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}-2+1)$
6356097	$9*((8+(7^6+54)*3)^2-1)$	7077869	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7-(6-5)^{\wedge}4)*3-2)-1$
6356115	$9*((8+(7^6+54)*3)^2+1)$	7077907	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7-(6-5)^{\wedge}4)*3+2)+1$
6369781	$-9*8+7^6*(54+3/21)$	7098157	$(9/(8+7^6*543-2))^{\wedge}-1$
6369836	$-9-8+7^6*(54+3/21)$	7138232	$(9+8)*(-7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
6369852	$-9+8+7^6*(54+3/21)$	7138266	$(9+8)*(-7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
6369854	$9-8+7^6*(54+3/21)$	7138470	$(9+8)*(7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
6369870	$9+8+7^6*(54+3/21)$	7138504	$(9+8)*(7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
6369925	$9*8+7^6*(54+3/21)$	7147197	$9/8*(7^6*54-3+21)$
6386723	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4)*3^2)-1$	7147287	$(-98-7^6*54)/(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
6386725	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4)*3^2)+1$	7160517	$(98-7)*(6*5^{\wedge}4-3)*21$
6386867	$9*(8+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4)*3^2)-1$	7163776	$9^{\wedge}8-7^6*5*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
6386869	$9*(8+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4)*3^2)+1$	7166800	$98*((7/(6+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$
6405280	$98*((7^6*5+4)/3^{\wedge}2-1)$	7166996	$98*((7/(6+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
6405476	$98*((7^6*5+4)/3^{\wedge}2+1)$	7171983	$(98-7)*(6*5^{\wedge}4+3)*21$
6456379	$(9+8)*(7^6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	7176186	$-98+(7^6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
6456413	$(9+8)*(7^6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	7176212	$-9*8+(7^6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
6456549	$(9+8)*(7^6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	7176356	$9*8+(7^6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
6469903	$(9*8-7^6*5)*(-4-3*2-1)$	7176382	$98+(7^6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
6471487	$(9*8+7^6*5)*(4^3-2+1)$	7176796	$-98+(7^6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
6578449	$(-9+8*7)*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)/2-1)$	7176822	$-9*8+(7^6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
6578543	$(-9+8*7)*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)/2+1)$	7176966	$9*8+(7^6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
6585131	$(-9+8*(7^6-54)/3)*21$	7176992	$98+(7^6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
6585509	$(9+8*(7^6-54)/3)*21$	7281425	$9^{\wedge}8-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4-321)$
6588223	$-9+8*((7^6-5)*(4+3)+21)$	7293937	$9+8*(7^6-5)/4*(32-1)$
6588241	$9+8*((7^6-5)*(4+3)+21)$	7294557	$9+8*(7^6+5)/4*(32-1)$
6588465	$9+8*((7^6+5)*(4+3)-21)$	7300648	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
6591179	$(-9+8*(7^6+54)/3)*21$	7300666	$9+(8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
6591557	$(9+8*(7^6+54)/3)*21$	7335648	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
6639894	$(-9-8)*(7*6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	7335666	$9+(8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$
6639928	$(-9-8)*(7*6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	7370454	$(-98+(7^6-5^{\wedge}4)*3)*21$
6641322	$(9+8)*(7*6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	7372335	$-9-(8-(7^6-5^{\wedge}4)*3)*21$
6641356	$(9+8)*(7*6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	7372353	$9-(8-(7^6-5^{\wedge}4)*3)*21$
6656299	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3))^2-1)$	7372414	$-98+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4)*3*21$
6656333	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3))^2+1)$	7372610	$98+(7^6-5^{\wedge}4)*3*21$
6665103	$9*(8*7^6-5^{\wedge}4*321)$	7372671	$-9+(8+(7^6-5^{\wedge}4)*3)*21$
6666805	$(9+8)*((7^6*5+4)/3^2-1)$	7372689	$9+(8+(7^6-5^{\wedge}4)*3)*21$
6666839	$(9+8)*((7^6*5+4)/3^2+1)$	7374570	$(98+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4)*3)*21$
6693180	$9^{\wedge}8-7^6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$	7379398	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7/6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
6693994	$9+(8/(7+65^{\wedge}4*3-2))^{\wedge}-1$	7379416	$9+(8^{\wedge}7/6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
6750135	$9/8*(7^6*(54-3)+21)$	7383366	$9*876*(5^{\wedge}4*3/2-1)$
6821241	$-9-(8-7*6)*5^{\wedge}4*321$	7399134	$9*876*(5^{\wedge}4*3/2+1)$
6821259	$9-(8-7*6)*5^{\wedge}4*321$	7408128	$(-9-8+(7^6-54)*3)*21$
6902038	$(9/((8/7^{\wedge}-6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$	7408308	$-9-(8-(7^6-54)*3)*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
7408326	$9 - (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * 3) * 21$	7542724	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21$
7408464	$(-9 + 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * 3) * 21$	7544536	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * (3 + 21)$
7408506	$(9 - 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * 3) * 21$	7548911	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 - 1)$
7408569	$(-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	7550161	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 + 1)$
7408644	$-9 + (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * 3) * 21$	7553952	$(9 + 87) * (6 * 5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21$
7408662	$9 + (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * 3) * 21$	7566048	$(9 + 87) * (6 * 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21$
7408842	$(9 + 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * 3) * 21$	7567991	$-9 + (876 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
7409262	$(-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 3) * 21$	7567992	$-9 + (876 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 * 1$
7409766	$(-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * 3) * 21$	7567993	$-9 + (876 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$
7409892	$(-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * 3) * 21$	7568009	$9 + (876 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
7410396	$(-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * 3) * 21$	7568010	$9 + (876 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 * 1$
7410468	$9 - (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	7568011	$9 + (876 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$
7410804	$9 + (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	7568911	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 * 21$
7411161	$9 - (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 3) * 21$	7581520	$98 * ((7 / (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 + 3))^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
7411474	$-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 - 2 + 1)$	7581716	$98 * ((7 / (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 + 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
7412001	$9 + (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * 3) * 21$	7587940	$-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$
7412300	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 - 2 + 1)$	7587966	$-9 * 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$
7412631	$9 + (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * 3) * 21$	7588110	$9 * 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$
7412988	$9 - (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	7588136	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$
7413306	$-9 + (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	7588611	$-9 * 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$
7413324	$9 + (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	7588755	$9 * 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$
7413378	$(98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 3) * 21$	7588781	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$
7413882	$(98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * 3) * 21$	7623785	$(-9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 / 5) * (4 + 321)$
7414008	$(98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * 3) * 21$	7641660	$(-9 - 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 / 5) * (4 + 321)$
7414512	$(98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * 3) * 21$	7644576	$-9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 / 5) * (4 + 321)$
7414932	$(-9 - 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * 3) * 21$	7644594	$9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 / 5) * (4 + 321)$
7415112	$-9 - (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * 3) * 21$	7645470	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) / 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
7415130	$9 - (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * 3) * 21$	7645666	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) / 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$
7415205	$(98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	7646762	$-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1)$
7415268	$(-9 + 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * 3) * 21$	7646788	$-9 * 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1)$
7415310	$(9 - 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * 3) * 21$	7646932	$9 * 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1)$
7415448	$-9 + (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * 3) * 21$	7646958	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1)$
7415466	$9 + (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * 3) * 21$	7647412	$-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1)$
7415646	$(9 + 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * 3) * 21$	7647438	$-9 * 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1)$
7449204	$(-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	7647582	$9 * 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1)$
7451085	$-9 - (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	7647608	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1)$
7451103	$9 - (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	7649776	$-9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 / 5) * (4 + 321)$
7451164	$-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 * 21$	7649794	$9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 / 5) * (4 + 321)$
7451360	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 * 21$	7652710	$(9 + 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 / 5) * (4 + 321)$
7451421	$-9 + (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	7653428	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}3 * 2) - 1$
7451439	$9 + (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	7653430	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}3 * 2) + 1$
7453320	$(98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	7653572	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}3 * 2) - 1$
7469964	$9 * (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4(4 + 3)) * 21)$	7653574	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}3 * 2) + 1$
7470108	$9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4(4 + 3)) * 21)$	7670585	$(9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 / 5) * (4 + 321)$
7470296	$-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 - 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$	7670852	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 * 21)$
7470322	$-9 * 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 - 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$	7686385	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 / 4) / 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
7470466	$9 * 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 - 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$	7686581	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 / 4) / 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$
7470492	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 - 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$	7687610	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) / 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
7470931	$-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 - 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$	7687806	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) / 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$
7470957	$-9 * 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 - 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$	7703094	$98 * 7 * (6 / 5^{\wedge}4 - 4^{\wedge}3 - 21)$
7471101	$9 * 8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 - 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$	7746606	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4(4 + 3))^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
7471127	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 - 2^{\wedge}4 - 1)$	7746802	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4(4 + 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
7490161	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 * 21$	7764495	$-9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 * (32 + 1)$
7508911	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 + 1)$	7764513	$9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 * (32 + 1)$
7510161	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 - 1)$	7764736	$-98 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3 - 2 - 1)$
7514536	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * (3 + 21)$	7764932	$98 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3 - 2 - 1)$
7516348	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21$	7765173	$9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) / 4 * (32 + 1)$
7516474	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21$	7808949	$-9 / 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3) + 2 + 1)$
7518286	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * (3 - 21)$	7825627	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4^{\wedge}3(3^{\wedge}2 + 1))$
7526071	$-9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	7863786	$9 * 8 * -7 + 6 * 5 * (4^{\wedge}3 * 2 - 1)$
7526089	$9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	7863810	$9 * 8 * -7 + 6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 2 - 1)$
7529095	$-9 + (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	7863822	$9 * 8 * -7 + 6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 2 + 1)$
7529097	$-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4^{\wedge}3 - 21$	7863846	$9 * 8 * -7 + 6 * 5 * (4^{\wedge}3 * 2 + 1)$
7529113	$9 + (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	7864155	$-9 * (8 + 7) + 6 * 5 * (4^{\wedge}3 * 2 - 1)$
7529888	$-9 * (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) + 4) * (3^{\wedge}4 - 2 - 1)$	7864179	$-9 * (8 + 7) + 6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 2 - 1)$
7529959	$-9 + (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	7864191	$-9 * (8 + 7) + 6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 2 + 1)$
7529975	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4^{\wedge}3 + 21$	7864461	$9 * (8 + 7) + 6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 2 + 1)$
7529977	$9 + (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	7864794	$9 * 8 * 7 + 6 * 5 * (4^{\wedge}3 * 2 - 1)$
7532983	$-9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	7864818	$9 * 8 * 7 + 6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 2 - 1)$
7533001	$9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	7864830	$9 * 8 * 7 + 6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 2 + 1)$
7540786	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * (3 - 21)$	7864854	$9 * 8 * 7 + 6 * 5 * (4^{\wedge}3 * 2 + 1)$
7542598	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21$	7882050	$-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 + 3 * 21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
7882246	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3*21)$	8436979	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3^*2)+1$
7882720	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3*21)$	8447895	$9*(87*6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
7882916	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3*21)$	8447913	$9*(87*6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
7994335	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-321)$	8453664	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3-21)$
7995015	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-321)$	8455539	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)-21)$
7999333	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	8455709	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)-2)-1$
7999622	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	8455711	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)-2)+1$
7999656	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3^{\wedge}2+1)$	8455745	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)+2)-1$
7999673	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3*2-1)$	8455747	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)+2)+1$
7999724	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3-2+1)$	8455917	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)+21)$
7999758	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3+2-1)$	8459423	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)-1$
7999826	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3-2+1)$	8459425	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)+1$
7999860	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3+2-1)$	8459531	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)-1$
7999962	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	8459533	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)+1$
8000013	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	8468151	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-321)$
8000060	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	8468169	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-321)$
8000204	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	8468664	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3-21)$
8000230	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	8469042	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3+21)$
8000251	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	8470929	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3+21)$
8000302	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	8472414	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3-21)$
8000404	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3-2+1)$	8472792	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3+21)$
8000438	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3+2-1)$	8473287	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+321)$
8000506	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3-2+1)$	8473305	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+321)$
8000540	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3+2-1)$	8481923	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)-1$
8000591	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3*2+1)$	8481925	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)+1$
8000608	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	8482031	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)-1$
8000642	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	8482033	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)+1$
8000931	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	8485539	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)-21)$
8005249	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+321)$	8485709	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)-2)-1$
8005929	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+321)$	8485711	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)-2)+1$
8031933	$-9*((8-76)*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$	8485745	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)+2)-1$
8116353	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6-6-5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$	8485747	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)+2)+1$
8117565	$(9*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3))*(-2-1)$	8485917	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)+21)$
8117662	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-21$	8487792	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$
8117704	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+21$	8504477	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6-6+5^{\wedge}4*3*2)-1$
8117858	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-21$	8504479	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6-6+5^{\wedge}4*3*2)+1$
8117900	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+21$	8521077	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3/21))$
8117997	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3))*(2+1)$	8521221	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3/21))$
8130854	$(9/(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	8571978	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(3-21))$
8158130	$(9+8)/7/(6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3-2)^{\wedge}-1$	8588286	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
8170071	$(9/(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4+3*2))^{\wedge}-1$	8589420	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$
8170622	$(-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)*5^{\wedge}4/3)/(2+1)$	8605539	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)-21)$
8170628	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)*5^{\wedge}4/3)/(2+1)$	8605709	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)-2)-1$
8205597	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(32-1))$	8605711	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)-2)+1$
8233372	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4+3)-21)$	8605745	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)+2)-1$
8235136	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4+3)-2-1)$	8605747	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)+2)+1$
8235178	$(9*8-7^{\wedge}6*5*4)*(-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	8605917	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)+21)$
8235381	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	8640641	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
8235479	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	8640675	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
8235682	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	8644776	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*3-21)$
8235724	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4+3)+2+1)$	8645103	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
8237488	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4+3)+21)$	8645511	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4*3-21)$
8262135	$(98+7)^*(6*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$	8646785	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
8275365	$(98+7)^*(6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$	8646883	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
8285103	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$	8647520	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
8290719	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	8647618	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
8290737	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	8648892	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*3+21)$
8296353	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$	8649627	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4*3+21)$
8335539	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)-21)$	8656353	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$
8335709	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)-2)-1$	8734995	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(32+1))$
8335711	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)-2)+1$	8735139	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(32+1))$
8335745	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)+2)-1$	8792307	$9*87*(6/5^{\wedge}-4*3-21)$
8335747	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)+2)+1$	8817201	$9*(-87+6^{\wedge}(5+4-3)^*21)$
8335917	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)+21)$	8818767	$9*(87+6^{\wedge}(5+4-3)^*21)$
8352036	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$	8822595	$(9*-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4*3+2+1)$
8353170	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$	8823773	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4*3+2+1)$
8369478	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3-21))$	8824755	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4*3+2+1)$
8431388	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*43/(2+1)$	8825103	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6-6+5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
8431406	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*43/(2+1)$	8886053	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
8431500	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*43)/(2+1)$	8964648	$98*7*(6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
8431518	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*43)/(2+1)$	9000106	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)/2-1)$
8436977	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6-6-5^{\wedge}4*3*2)-1$	9000140	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)/2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
9000157	$(9+8)*((7^6*(5+4)+3)/2-1)$	9525276	$9*(8+(7^6-54)*3^2+1)$
9000191	$(9+8)*((7^6*(5+4)+3)/2+1)$	9526338	$9*((-8+7^6/5)*(43+2)+1)$
9042852	$98*7*(-6+(5^4+3)*21)$	9527876	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)*3^2)-1$
9043895	$-9*(8+(7/6-5)*4^3^2)-1$	9527878	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)*3^2)+1$
9043897	$-9*(8+(7/6-5)*4^3^2)+1$	9528020	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*3^2)-1$
9051084	$98*7*(6+(5^4+3)*21)$	9528022	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*3^2)+1$
9056915	$(-98+7^6*(5-4/3))^*21$	9529074	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4)-3^*21)$
9058814	$9-(8-7^6*(5-4/3))^*21$	9529176	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4))-321$
9058875	$-98+7^6*(5-4/3)^*21$	9529281	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4)-3-21)$
9059071	$98+7^6*(5-4/3)^*21$	9529320	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4))-321$
9059132	$-9+(8+7^6*(5-4/3))^*21$	9529442	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4)-3^*2)-1$
9059150	$9+(8+7^6*(5-4/3))^*21$	9529444	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4)-3^*2)+1$
9061031	$(98+7^6*(5-4/3))^*21$	9529550	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4)+3^*2)-1$
9129050	$-98+(7/(6-(5^4)^3)^2)^{\wedge}-1$	9529588	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4)*3^2)+1$
9129076	$-9*8+(7/(6-(5^4)^3)^2)^{\wedge}-1$	9529694	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4)+3^*2)-1$
9129220	$9*8+(7/(6-(5^4)^3)^2)^{\wedge}-1$	9529696	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4)+3^*2)+1$
9129246	$98+(7/(6-(5^4)^3)^2)^{\wedge}-1$	9529794	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4)+32+1)$
9174893	$-98-7*(6-5^4^3^2+1)$	9529818	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4))+321$
9174935	$-98-7*(6-5*(4^3^2+1))$	9529857	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4)+3+21)$
9175103	$98-7*(6-5^4^3^2-1)$	9529962	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4))+321$
9175131	$98-7*(6-5*(4^3^2+1))$	9530064	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4)+3^*21)$
9175145	$98+7*(6+5*(4^3^2-1))$	9531116	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)*3^2)-1$
9175173	$98+7*(6+5^4^3^2-1)$	9531118	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)*3^2)+1$
9175187	$98+7*(6+5^4^3^2+1)$	9531260	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3^2)-1$
9176549	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4/3+2))-1$	9531262	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3^2)+1$
9176551	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4/3+2))+1$	9532800	$9*((8+7^6/5)*(43+2)-1)$
9176693	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4/3+2))-1$	9532818	$9*((8+7^6/5)*(43+2)+1)$
9176695	$9*(8+7^6*(5*(4/3)+2))+1$	9533862	$9*(-8+(7^6+54)*3^2-1)$
9223662	$98*(7^6/5^4-(3+2)^{\wedge}-1)$	9533880	$9*(-8+(7^6+54)*3^2+1)$
9359532	$(-9+87)*6*(5^4*32-1)$	9534006	$9*(8+(7^6+54)*3^2-1)$
9360468	$(-9+87)*6*(5^4*32+1)$	9534024	$9*(8+(7^6+54)*3^2+1)$
9397215	$9/8*(7^6*(5+4^3+2)+1)$	9629935	$-9-8*(7-6*5^4*321)$
9407591	$-9+8*(7^6-54)*(3^2+1)$	9629953	$9-8*(7-6*5^4*321)$
9407609	$9+8*(7^6-54)*(3^2+1)$	9630047	$-9+8*(7+6*5^4*321)$
9411233	$9+8*(7^6*5-43)^*2-1$	9630065	$9+8*(7+6*5^4*321)$
9411371	$-9+(8*7^6-54)*(3^2+1)$	9630852	$98*(7^6-5^4*(32-1))$
9411389	$9+(8*7^6-54)*(3^2+1)$	9699219	$-9*8+(7+6*5)^*(4^3^2-1)$
9411632	$(9-8-7^6*5^4)*(-3-2+1)$	9699267	$-98+(7^6-5)^*(4^3^2+1)$
9411756	$(9+(8-7^6*5)^4)*(-3-2+1)$	9699293	$-9*8+(7+6*5)^*(4^3^2+1)$
9411874	$(9+8*(7^6*5-4))/(3/2-1)$	9699363	$9*8+(7+6*5)^*(4^3^2-1)$
9411966	$(-9+8*(7^6*5+4))/(3/2-1)$	9699389	$98+(7^6-5)^*(4^3^2-1)$
9412084	$(9+(8+7^6*5)^4)*(3+2-1)$	9699463	$98+(7^6-5)^*(4^3^2+1)$
9412208	$(9*8+7^6*5^4)*(3+2-1)$	9721637	$(9+8)*(7^6*5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$
9412451	$-9+(8*7^6+54)*(3^2+1)$	9799812	$9*876*((5^4-3)^*2-1)$
9412469	$9+(8*7^6+54)*(3^2+1)$	9815580	$9*876*((5^4-3)^*2+1)$
9412609	$9+8*((7^6*5+43)^*2-1)$	9875852	$98*(7^6-5^4*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
9416231	$-9+8*(7^6+54)*(3^2+1)$	9880458	$(-98+7^6*(5-4+3))^*21$
9416249	$9+8*(7^6+54)*(3^2+1)$	9881874	$9-(8-(7^6-5)^*4+3)^*21$
9417819	$(-9*8+(7^6-5)/4)^*321$	9882000	$9-(8-(7^6-5)^*4-3)^*21$
9429093	$(9-8*7)*(6-5^4*321)$	9882357	$9-(8-7^6*(5-4+3))^*21$
9429657	$(-9+8*7)*(6+5^4*321)$	9882693	$9+(8+7^6*(5-4+3))^*21$
9435474	$(-9-8+(7^6-5)/4)^*321$	9883050	$9+(8+(7^6+5)^*4-3)^*21$
9438372	$9-(8-(7^6-5)/4)^*321$	9883158	$-9+(8+(7^6+5)^*4+3)^*21$
9440610	$(-9+8+(7^6-5)/4)^*321$	9884574	$(98+7^6*(5-4+3))^*21$
9440859	$-9*8+(7^6-5)/4^*321$	9894420	$9*876*((5^4+3)^*2-1)$
9440914	$-9-8+(7^6-5)/4^*321$	9910188	$9*876*((5^4+3)^*2+1)$
9440930	$-9+8+(7^6-5)/4^*321$	9910719	$9*(8*(7^6+5^4*32)-1)$
9440932	$9-8+(7^6-5)/4^*321$	9910737	$9*(8*(7^6+5^4*32)+1)$
9440948	$9+8+(7^6-5)/4^*321$	9921933	$9*((8+76)^*5^4-3)^*21$
9441003	$9*8+(7^6-5)/4^*321$	9923067	$9*((8+76)^*5^4+3)^*21$
9441252	$(9-8+(7^6-5)/4)^*321$	9930516	$(9+8)*(7^6*5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
9443490	$-9+(8+(7^6-5)/4)^*321$	9930550	$(9+8)*(7^6*5-(4^3)^2+1)$
9443508	$9+(8+(7^6-5)/4)^*321$	9947023	$(9+8)*((7^6-5^4)^*(3+2)-1)$
9446388	$(9+8+(7^6-5)/4)^*321$	9947057	$(9+8)*((7^6-5^4)^*(3+2)+1)$
9464043	$(9*8+(7^6-5)/4)^*321$	9970789	$(9+8)*(7^6*5-(4^3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
9508352	$98*(7^6-5^4*(32+1))$	9978337	$(9+8)*7^6*5-4^*321$
9517688	$(-9-8)*(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2+1$	9982740	$(9+8)*(7^6*5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
9517722	$(-9-8)*(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2-1$	9982774	$(9+8)*(7^6*5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
9517960	$(9+8)*(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))^*2+1$	9992804	$(9+8)*(7^6*5-432-1)$
9525114	$9*(-8+(7^6-54)*3^2-1)$	9992820	$(9+8)*(7^6*5-432)-1$
9525132	$9*(-8+(7^6-54)*3^2+1)$	9992821	$(9+8)*(7^6*5-432)^{\wedge}1$
9525258	$9*(8+(7^6-54)*3^2-1)$	9992822	$(9+8)*(7^6*5-432)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
9992838	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 432 + 1)$	10239670	$-9 + (8^{(-7/6)}/5)^{-4} - 321$
9994640	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4 - 321)$	10239688	$9 + (8^{(-7/6)}/5)^{-4} - 321$
9994776	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4 - 321)$	10240312	$-9 + (8^{(-7/6)}/5)^{-4} + 321$
9996901	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4^3 * (2+1))$	10240330	$9 + (8^{(-7/6)}/5)^{-4} + 321$
9997700	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - (4*3)^2 - 1)$	10249526	$98 * (7^6 - (5^4 - 3) * 21)$
9997734	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - (4*3)^2 + 1)$	10259487	$(-9 + 87 * 6) * (5^4 * 32 - 1)$
9998329	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4 * 3^2 + 1)$	10260513	$(-9 + 87 * 6) * (5^4 * 32 + 1)$
9998448	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5^4) * (3+2) - 1)$	10276353	$9 * (8 * 7^6 + 5^4 * 321)$
9998482	$(9+8) * ((7^6 - 5^4) * (3+2) + 1)$	10278693	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 * 2 + 1)$
9999060	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4^3 - 2 + 1)$	10298475	$(-9 + 8/7) * (6 - 5 * 4^3 * 2 - 1)$
9999094	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4^3 + 2 - 1)$	10321506	$9 * 87 * (-6 + (5^4 + 3) * 21)$
9999128	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4^3 + 2 + 1)$	10330902	$9 * 87 * (6 + (5^4 + 3) * 21)$
9999315	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - (4+3)^2 - 1)$	10353085	$(-9 + 8 * 7^6 * (5 - 4/3)) * (2+1)$
9999349	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - (4+3)^2 + 1)$	10353139	$(9 + 8 * 7^6 * (5 - 4/3)) * (2+1)$
9999413	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 43) - 21$	10398339	$(9 - 8 * (7/6 - 5)) * (4^3 * 2 - 1)$
9999455	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 43) + 21$	10427102	$98 * (7^6 + 5^4 * (3 - 21))$
9999642	$-98 + (7^6 - 5) * (4^3 + 21)$	10439469	$-9 + 87 * 6 * (5^4 * 32 - 1)$
9999756	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4 * 3 * 2) - 1$	10439487	$9 + 87 * 6 * (5^4 * 32 - 1)$
9999758	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4 * 3 * 2) + 1$	10440513	$-9 + 87 * 6 * (5^4 * 32 + 1)$
9999776	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4) - 321$	10440531	$9 + 87 * 6 * (5^4 * 32 + 1)$
9999838	$98 + (7^6 - 5) * (4^3 + 21)$	10485121	$9 - 8 * (76 - 5 * (4^3 * 2 - 1))$
9999842	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4 * (3+2) + 1)$	10485135	$-9 - 8 * (76 - 5 * 4^3 * 2 + 1)$
9999912	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4) - 321$	10485153	$9 - 8 * (76 - 5 * 4^3 * 2 + 1)$
9999978	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4 - 3 * 2 - 1)$	10485183	$-9 - 8 * (76 - 5 * (4^3 * 2 + 1))$
10000352	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4 + 3 * 2 + 1)$	10485201	$9 - 8 * (76 - 5 * (4^3 * 2 + 1))$
10000418	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4) + 321$	10485911	$9 * ((8^7/6 + 5) * (4/3 + 2)) + 1$
10000420	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4 * 3 + 2 + 1)$	10486337	$9 + 8 * (76 + 5 * (4^3 * 2 - 1))$
10000488	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4 * (3+2) - 1)$	10486385	$9 + 8 * (76 + 5 * 4^3 * 2 + 1)$
10000492	$-98 + (7^6 + 5) * (4^3 + 21)$	10486399	$-9 + 8 * (76 + 5 * (4^3 * 2 + 1))$
10000554	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4) + 321$	10486417	$9 + 8 * (76 + 5 * (4^3 * 2 + 1))$
10000572	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4 * 3 * 2) - 1$	10565298	$9 * 8 * (7^6 * 5/4 - 321)$
10000574	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4 * 3 * 2) + 1$	10573101	$(-9 + 8 * (7/6 + 5)) * (4^3 * 2 - 1)$
10000688	$98 + (7^6 + 5) * (4^3 + 21)$	10583478	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 - 54) * (3^2 + 1))$
10000875	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 43) - 21$	10583622	$9 * (8 + (7^6 - 54) * (3^2 + 1))$
10000917	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 43) + 21$	10585521	$9 * (8 * 7^6 * 5/4 - 321)$
10000981	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + (4+3)^2 - 1)$	10586115	$9 * (8 * (7^6 * 5/4 - 32) + 1)$
10001015	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + (4+3)^2 + 1)$	10587185	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 * 5 - 4^3) * 2) - 1$
10001202	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 - 2 - 1)$	10587187	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 * 5 - 4^3) * 2) + 1$
10001236	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 - 2 + 1)$	10587329	$9 * (8 + (7^6 * 5 - 4^3) * 2) - 1$
10001270	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 + 2 - 1)$	10587331	$9 * (8 + (7^6 * 5 - 4^3) * 2) + 1$
10001848	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4) * (3+2) - 1)$	10587789	$9 * ((8 + 7^6 * 5 - 43) * 2 + 1)$
10001882	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4) * (3+2) + 1)$	10588313	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 * 5 - 4/3) * 2) - 1$
10002001	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4 * 3^2 + 1)$	10588315	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 * 5 - 4/3) * 2) + 1$
10002596	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + (4*3)^2 - 1)$	10588319	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 * 5 - 4 + 3) * 2) - 1$
10002630	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + (4*3)^2 + 1)$	10588361	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4/3) * 2) - 1$
10003429	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 * (2+1))$	10588363	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4/3) * 2) + 1$
10005554	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4 + 321)$	10588457	$9 * (8 + (7^6 * 5 - 4/3) * 2) - 1$
10005690	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4 + 321)$	10588459	$9 * (8 + (7^6 * 5 - 4/3) * 2) + 1$
10007492	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 432 - 1)$	10588501	$9 * (8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4 - 3) * 2) + 1$
10007508	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 432) - 1$	10588505	$9 * (8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4/3) * 2) - 1$
10007509	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 432)^2$	10588507	$9 * (8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4/3) * 2) + 1$
10007510	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 432) + 1$	10589319	$9 * ((8 + 7^6 * 5 + 43) * 2 - 1)$
10007526	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 432 + 1)$	10589489	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4^3) * 2) - 1$
10017556	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 * (3+2) - 1)$	10589491	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4^3) * 2) + 1$
10017590	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 * (3+2) + 1)$	10589633	$9 * (8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4^3) * 2) - 1$
10021993	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 * 321)$	10589635	$9 * (8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4^3) * 2) + 1$
10029541	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + (4*3)^2 + 1)$	10591299	$9 * (8 * 7^6 * 5/4 + 321)$
10031241	$-9 + (8 * 7 - 6) * 5^4 * 321$	10593198	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 + 54) * (3^2 + 1))$
10031259	$9 + (8 * 7 - 6) * 5^4 * 321$	10593342	$9 * (8 + (7^6 + 54) * (3^2 + 1))$
10053273	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4) * (3+2) - 1)$	10611522	$9 * 8 * (7^6 * 5/4 + 321)$
10053307	$(9+8) * ((7^6 + 5^4) * (3+2) + 1)$	10619469	$(9 + 87 * 6) * (5^4 * 32 - 1)$
10056384	$9 * (8^7 - 6^8 * (5 + 4 - 3) * 21)$	10620531	$(9 + 87 * 6) * (5^4 * 32 + 1)$
10059602	$98 * (7^6 - 5^4 * (3 + 21))$	10696504	$98 * ((7 + 6)^5 - 4^3 * 2 - 1)$
10069780	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 * (3^2) - 1)$	10696700	$98 * ((7 + 6)^5 - 4^3 * 2 + 1)$
10069814	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 * (3^2) + 1)$	10737566	$-9 * (8 + 7^6 - 5 * 4^3 * 2) - 1$
10222848	$9 * 87 * (-6 + (5^4 - 3) * 21)$	10737568	$-9 * (8 + 7^6 - 5 * 4^3 * 2) + 1$
10232244	$9 * 87 * (6 + (5^4 - 3) * 21)$	10737710	$9 * (8 - 7^6 + 5 * 4^3 * 2) - 1$
10234930	$-98 + (7^6 - 5) * (43 * 2 + 1)$	10737712	$9 * (8 - 7^6 + 5 * 4^3 * 2) + 1$
10235126	$98 + (7^6 - 5) * (43 * 2 + 1)$	10768412	$(9 + 8) * ((7 + 6)^5 + 4^3 * 2 - 1)$
10235800	$-98 + (7^6 + 5) * (43 * 2 + 1)$	10768446	$(9 + 8) * ((7 + 6)^5 + 4^3 * 2 + 1)$
10235996	$98 + (7^6 + 5) * (43 * 2 + 1)$	10807416	$-9 - (8 + 7)^6 * (5^4 - 4 * 32 - 1)$
10237178	$98 * (7^6 - (5^4 + 3) * 21)$	10807434	$9 - (8 + 7)^6 * (5^4 - 4 * 32 - 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
10829663	$9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	11343794	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3-21)$
10829665	$9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	11344970	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)*(2+1))$
10830383	$9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	11345558	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3-2-1)$
10830385	$9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	11345754	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3-2+1)$
10833615	$-9^*(8+7-6*5^{\wedge}4*321)$	11345803	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
10833741	$-9^*(8-7-6*5^{\wedge}4*321)$	11345831	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)-21$
10833885	$9^*(8+7+6*5^{\wedge}4*321)$	11345873	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)+21$
10834254	$9^*(8*7+6/5^{\wedge}-4*321)$	11345901	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
10840443	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}43/21)$	11345950	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3+2-1)$
10840587	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}43/21)$	11346146	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1)$
10917102	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$	11346734	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)*(2+1))$
10919454	$(98-7)^*6*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	11376477	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(3/2+1))$
10919909	$(98-7)^*(6*5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	11406416	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$
10920091	$(98-7)^*(6*5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	11406612	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$
10920546	$(98-7)^*6*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	11407592	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$
10985058	$9^*((87+6)*5^{\wedge}4-3)*21$	11407788	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$
10986192	$9^*((87+6)*5^{\wedge}4+3)*21$	11411855	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*((5+43)*2+1)$
10999697	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3/2)-1)$	11412051	$98+7^{\wedge}6*((5+43)*2+1)$
10999731	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3/2)+1)$	11437629	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3/2-1)$
11000632	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3/2)-1)$	11498928	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1)$
11000666	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3/2)+1)$	11508977	$98^*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(32+1)$
11009747	$-98-7^*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	11510227	$98^*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(32-1)$
11009894	$98-7^*6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	11514602	$98^*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(3+21)$
11009929	$98-7^*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	11518352	$98^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3-21)$
11010042	$9^*8^{\wedge}7-6^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	11519424	$(9+87)^*6*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$
11010078	$9^*8^{\wedge}7-6^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	11520576	$(9+87)^*6*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$
11010202	$-98+7^*6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	11540852	$98^*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(3-21)$
11010314	$98+7^*6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	11544602	$98^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3+21)$
11010349	$98+7^*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	11548089	$9^*(8/-76+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
11010363	$98+7^*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	11548977	$98^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1)$
11010398	$98+7^*6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	11550227	$98^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1)$
11039602	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	11560276	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
11108816	$9^*(-8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4-3))^{\wedge}-2)-1$	11566891	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4/3-21)$
11108818	$9^*(-8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4-3))^{\wedge}-2)+1$	11568670	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4/3-21)$
11108960	$9^*(8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4-3))^{\wedge}-2)-1$	11621379	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3/2-1)$
11108962	$9^*(8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4-3))^{\wedge}-2)+1$	11621575	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3/2+1)$
11114277	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	11647349	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4*(3+2)-1)$
11162004	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3*2-1)$	11651416	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$
11162200	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3*2+1)$	11651612	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$
11175287	$(9^*-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4*(3+2)-1)$	11652592	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$
11176753	$98+7^{\wedge}6*((5+43)*2-1)$	11652788	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$
11178023	$(9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4*(3+2)-1)$	11682727	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3/2+1))$
11234655	$-9-8^*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*321)$	11712470	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*(2+1))$
11234673	$9-8^*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*321)$	11713058	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3-2-1)$
11235327	$-9+8^*7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*321)$	11713254	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3-2+1)$
11235345	$9+8^*7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*321)$	11713303	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
11284602	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1))$	11713331	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)-21$
11289527	$9^*(-8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2)-1$	11713373	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)+21$
11289529	$9^*(-8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2)+1$	11713401	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
11289671	$9^*(8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2)-1$	11713450	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3+2-1)$
11289673	$9^*(8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2)+1$	11713646	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1)$
11291472	$(-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4)^*(3+21)$	11714234	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)*(2+1))$
11292432	$(-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4)^*(3+21)$	11715410	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$
11293641	$9-(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4)^*(3+21)$	11732070	$98^*((7^{\wedge}6-(6+5+4)+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
11293665	$9+8^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4*3-21)$	11743977	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$
11293726	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4*(3+21)$	11764810	$(-9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*5/4)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
11293779	$(9+8^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3))^*(2+1)$	11774602	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1))$
11293869	$(-9+8^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3))^*(2+1)$	11788551	$-9^*(876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
11293922	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4*(3+21)$	11788587	$-9^*(876-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
11294001	$9+8^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4*3+21)$	11788595	$-9^*(876-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
11294013	$9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4/3+21)$	11788597	$-9^*(876-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
11294625	$9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4*3-21$	11788605	$-9^*(876-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
11294686	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4*(3+21)$	11788641	$-9^*(876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
11294739	$(9+8^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3))^*(2+1)$	11793455	$9^*(8^*7*-6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
11294829	$(-9+8^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3))^*(2+1)$	11793457	$9^*(8^*7*-6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
11294882	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4*(3+21)$	11795543	$-9^*(8^*(7+6))-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
11294961	$9+8^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4*3+21)$	11795598	$-9^*(87+6-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
11294967	$-9+(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4)^*(3+21)$	11795634	$9^*(-87-6+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
11294985	$9+(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4)^*(3+21)$	11795652	$9^*(-87-6+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
11296176	$(98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4)^*(3+21)$	11795688	$-9^*(87+6-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
11297136	$(98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4)^*(3+21)$	11795706	$-9^*(87-6-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
11315227	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	11795733	$-9^*(8+76-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
11795742	$9^*(-87+6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	12320743	$9^*-8+(7^*6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
11795760	$9^*(-87+6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	12320793	$9^*8+(7^*6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
11795769	$-9^*(8+76-5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	12320819	$98+(7^*6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
11795796	$-9^*(87-6-5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	12320862	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
11796173	$9^*(8-7^*6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	12320887	$9^*8+(7^*6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
11796407	$-9^*(8^*(7-6)-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	12320913	$98+(7^*6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
11796551	$9^*(8^*(7-6)+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	12321238	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
11796553	$9^*(8^*(7-6)+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	12321332	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
11796785	$-9^*(8-7^*6-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	12322131	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
11796787	$-9^*(8-7^*6-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	12339383	$(9+8^*76)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32-1)$
11797101	$-9^*(8-76-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	12340617	$(9+8^*76)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$
11797137	$-9^*(8-76-5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	12351624	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
11797362	$9^*(87+6+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	12351642	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
11797415	$9^*(8^*(7+6)+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	12351960	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
11797417	$9^*(8^*(7+6)+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	12351978	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
11799503	$9^*(8^*7^*6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	12352795	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^*3)^*21$
11799505	$9^*(8^*7^*6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	12352929	$(9^*-8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$
11801133	$9^*(87^*6+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	12352950	$(9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*(4+3))^*(-2-1)$
11801169	$9^*(87^*6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	12352958	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5+4/3)^*21$
11801187	$9^*(87^*6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	12352991	$98+(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^*3)^*21$
11801223	$9^*(87^*6+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	12353004	$(9-(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$
11801907	$9^*(8^*76+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	12353014	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5-4/3)^*21$
11801943	$9^*(8^*76+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	12353075	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4/3)^*21$
11801961	$9^*(8^*76+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	12353215	$98+(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4/3)^*21$
11801997	$9^*(8^*76+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	12353276	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5-4/3)^*21$
11804319	$9^*(876+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	12353286	$(-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$
11804355	$9^*(876+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	12353294	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5-4/3)^*21$
11804363	$9^*(876+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	12353299	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^*3)^*21$
11804365	$9^*(876+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	12353332	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5+4/3)^*21$
11804373	$9^*(876+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	12353340	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$
11804409	$9^*(876+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	12353350	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5+4/3)^*21$
11882647	$98+7^{\wedge}6^*((54-3)^*2-1)$	12353361	$(9^*8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$
11897004	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^*3^*2-1)$	12353495	$98+(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^*3)^*21$
11897200	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^*3^*2+1)$	12354312	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
11955249	$(9-8^*7)^*(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	12354330	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
11955343	$(9-8^*7)^*(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	12354648	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
11979401	$(-9+8^*76)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32-1)$	12354666	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
11980599	$(-9+8^*76)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$	12358445	$(9-8/7)^*(6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
11998141	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^*4)^*3^*2-1)$	12382233	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7)^*6-5^{\wedge}4^*321$
11998175	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^*4)^*3^*2+1)$	12382341	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)^*6-5^{\wedge}4^*321$
11999263	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*3^*2-1)$	12438759	$9+(8^*7+6)^*5^{\wedge}4^*321$
11999671	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^*3/2-1)$	12479022	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3+2+1)$
11999705	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^*3/2+1)$	12549053	$(9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4^{\wedge}3)/(-2-1)$
12000113	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^*3^*2+1)$	12549059	$(9-(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4^{\wedge}3)/(2+1)$
12000147	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4-3)-2-1)$	12564080	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
12000171	$(-9+8^*7^{\wedge}6^*(5/4+3))^*(2+1)$	12564082	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
12000225	$(9+8^*7^{\wedge}6^*(5/4+3))^*(2+1)$	12599370	$(98+7)^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32-1)$
12000249	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4-3)+2+1)$	12599895	$(98+7)^*(6^*5^{\wedge}4^*32-1)$
12000283	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^*3^*2-1)$	12600105	$(98+7)^*(6^*5^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$
12000691	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^*3/2-1)$	12600630	$(98+7)^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$
12000725	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^*3/2+1)$	12632102	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^*(3-21))$
12001099	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*3^*2-1)$	12638925	$-9^*(8+7^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^*321))$
12001133	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*3^*2+1)$	12639069	$9^*(8-7^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^*321))$
12002221	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^*4)^*3^*2-1)$	12639681	$-9^*(8-7^*(6+5^{\wedge}4^*321))$
12019602	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^*(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	12639825	$9^*(8+7^*(6+5^{\wedge}4^*321))$
12063931	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3^*2-1)$	12686193	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
12063965	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3^*2+1)$	12686287	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
12117749	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^*((54-3)^*2+1)$	12700269	$9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*3/2+1)$
12117945	$98+7^{\wedge}6^*((54-3)^*2+1)$	12705317	$9^*((-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4)^*3-2)-1$
12142102	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$	12705319	$9^*((-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4)^*3-2)+1$
12173112	$9^*((87-6^*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	12705355	$9^*((-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4)^*3+2)-1$
12173130	$9^*((87-6^*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	12705353	$9^*((-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4)^*3+2)+1$
12234911	$(-9+8^*7^{\wedge}6/5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$	12705454	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
12236081	$(9+8^*7^{\wedge}6/5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$	12705650	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
12239388	$-9^*(8-76)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32-1)$	12705669	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^*3+21)$
12240612	$-9^*(8-76)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$	12705896	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6^*54)^*(3-2+1)$
12252205	$98^*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	12705994	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^*54/(3/2-1)$
12252401	$98^*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3/2+1)$	12706003	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4+3)-2)+1$
12319311	$(9-8^*7)^*(6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	12706037	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4+3)+2)-1$
12319405	$(9-8^*7)^*(6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	12706039	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4+3)+2)+1$
12320649	$9^*-8+(7^*6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	12706117	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*54)^*(3-2+1)$
12320674	$(9-8^*7)^*(6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	12706145	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4+3)-2)-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
12706147	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4+3)-2)+1$	14000809	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*(4+3)-2+1)$
12706181	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4+3)+2)-1$	14000843	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*(4+3)+2-1)$
12706190	$98+7^6*54/(3/2-1)$	14000877	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*(4+3)+2+1)$
12706288	$(98+7^6*54)*(3-2+1)$	14105067	$9^8-7^6*(5*(4+3)^2+1)$
12706534	$-98+(7^6+5)*4*3^2(2+1)$	14116317	$(-9+8*(7^6*5-4^3))*(2+1)$
12706730	$98+(7^6+5)*4*3^2(2+1)$	14116371	$(9+8*(7^6*5-4^3))*(2+1)$
12706749	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)*4*3+2+1)$	14116857	$9+8*(7^6*5-4^3)*(2+1)$
12706829	$9*((8+(7^6+5)*4)*3-2)-1$	14117565	$(-9+8*(7^6*5-4^3))*(2+1)$
12706831	$9*((8+(7^6+5)*4)*3-2)+1$	14117619	$(9+8*(7^6*5-4^3))*(2+1)$
12706865	$9*((8+(7^6+5)*4)*3+2)-1$	14117625	$9+8*((7^6*5-4)*3-2+1)$
12706867	$9*((8+(7^6+5)*4)*3+2)+1$	14117685	$(-9+8*(7^6*5-4-3))*(2+1)$
12783483	$(-9+8^7)*6+5^4*321$	14117686	$-98+(7^6*5-4)*(3+2+1)$
12783591	$(9+8^7)*6+5^4*321$	14117739	$(9+8*(7^6*5-4-3))*(2+1)$
12809678	$98*(7^6+(5^4-3)*21)$	14117821	$(-9+8*(7^6*5-4^3))*(2+1)$
12822026	$98*(7^6+(5^4+3)*21)$	14117829	$(-9+8*(7^6*5-4+3))*(2+1)$
12855248	$9*(-8+7^6+5*4^3)^2-1$	14117931	$(9+8*(7^6*5+4-3))*(2+1)$
12855250	$9*(-8+7^6+5*4^3)^2+1$	14117939	$(9+8*(7^6*5+4+3))*(2+1)$
12855392	$9*(8+7^6+5*4^3)^2-1$	14118021	$(-9+8*(7^6*5+4+3))*(2+1)$
12855394	$9*(8+7^6+5*4^3)^2+1$	14118074	$98+(7^6*5+4)*(3+2+1)$
12941223	$9-(8-7^6*5)*(43-21)$	14118141	$(-9+8*(7^6*5+4^3))*(2+1)$
12941575	$9+(8+7^6*5)*(43-21)$	14118153	$9+8*((7^6*5+4)*3+2+1)$
12969080	$9*(-8^7+(6+5^4*3)^2)-1$	14118165	$9*(8*(7^6*5+4)/3+2+1)$
12969082	$9*(-8^7+(6+5^4*3)^2)+1$	14118195	$(9+8*(7^6*5+4^3))*(2+1)$
13040235	$(9*8-7)*(-6+5^4*321)$	14118921	$9+8*(7^6*5+4^3)*(2+1)$
13041015	$(9*8-7)*(6+5^4*321)$	14119389	$(-9+8*(7^6*5+4^3))*(2+1)$
13048946	$(9/(8^7(7+6-5)*(4+3)+2))^{\wedge}-1$	14119443	$(9+8*(7^6*5+4^3))*(2+1)$
13107159	$9-(8+7-65)*(4^3^2-1)$	14154669	$-9*(87+6*(5-4^3^2+1))$
13107241	$-9-(8+7-65)*(4^3^2+1)$	14154714	$-9*(87+6*(5-4^3^2)+1)$
13135283	$(-98+7^6*5)*(4/3+2+1)$	14154732	$-9*(87+6*(5-4^3^2)-1)$
13137302	$9-(8-7^6*5)*(4/3+2+1)$	14154777	$-9*(87+6*(5-4^3^2-1))$
13156851	$(-9+8^7)*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4^3)-2-1)$	14155001	$-9*(8^7+6*(5-4^3^2))-1$
13157133	$(-9+8^7)*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4^3)+2+1)$	14155209	$-9*(87-6*(5+4^3^2-1))$
13183352	$98*(7^6+5^4*3^2(2+1))$	14155254	$9*(-87+6*(5+4^3^2)-1)$
13294239	$-98+7^6*((54+3)*2-1)$	14155272	$9*(-87+6*(5+4^3^2)+1)$
13294395	$(9+8/7)*(-6+5^4*3^2+1)$	14155370	$-9*(8+7+6*(5-4^3^2))-1$
13294435	$98+7^6*((54+3)*2-1)$	14155372	$-9*(8+7+6*(5-4^3^2))+1$
13385272	$(9/(-8+(7^6-5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$	14155496	$-9*(8-7+6*(5-4^3^2))-1$
13387958	$-9-(8/(7-65^4*3)/2)^{\wedge}-1$	14155498	$-9*(8-7+6*(5-4^3^2))+1$
13387976	$9-(8/(7-65^4*3)/2)^{\wedge}-1$	14155514	$9*(8-7-6*(5-4^3^2))-1$
13411692	$(98+7^6*(5-43))*(2-1)$	14155541	$-9*(8^7-6*(5+4^3^2))-1$
13411971	$9-(8+7^6*(5-43))*(2+1)$	14155543	$-9*(8^7-6*(5+4^3^2))+1$
13412280	$(98-7^6*(5-43))*(2+1)$	14155703	$9*(-8+(7-6+5)*4^3^2)-1$
13428352	$98*(7^6+5^4*(32-1))$	14155705	$9*(-8+(7-6+5)*4^3^2)+1$
13490356	$9+(8*7^6-5)*43/(2+1)$	14155847	$9*(8+(7-6+5)*4^3^2)-1$
13491001	$9+8*(7^6+5)*43/(2+1)$	14155910	$-9*(8+7-6*(5+4^3^2))-1$
13529733	$98+7^6*((54+3)*2+1)$	14155912	$-9*(8+7-6*(5+4^3^2))+1$
13550852	$98*(7^6+5^4*(32+1))$	14156009	$9*(8^7-6*(5-4^3^2))-1$
13599320	$(98*7-6)*(5^4*32-1)$	14156011	$9*(8^7-6*(5-4^3^2))+1$
13600680	$(98*7-6)*(5^4*32+1)$	14156036	$-9*(8-7-6*(5+4^3^2))-1$
13671796	$-9*8+7*((6-5+4)^3^2-1)$	14156038	$-9*(8-7-6*(5+4^3^2))+1$
13671810	$-9*8+7*((6-5+4)^3^2+1)$	14156054	$9*(8-7+6*(5+4^3^2))-1$
13671940	$9*8+7*((6-5+4)^3^2-1)$	14156056	$9*(8-7+6*(5+4^3^2))+1$
13671954	$9*8+7*((6-5+4)^3^2+1)$	14156180	$9*(8+7+6*(5+4^3^2))-1$
13671966	$98+7*((6-5+4)^3^2-1)$	14156182	$9*(8+7+6*(5+4^3^2))+1$
13671980	$98+7*((6-5+4)^3^2+1)$	14156298	$9*(87-6*(5-4^3^2)+1)$
13679244	$-9*(8-7^6*(5^4*32-1))$	14156549	$9*(8^7+6*(5+4^3^2))-1$
13679388	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4*32-1))$	14156551	$9*(8^7+6*(5+4^3^2))+1$
13680612	$-9*(8-7^6*(5^4*32+1))$	14156883	$9*(87+6*(5+4^3^2+1))$
13680756	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4*32+1))$	14159922	$-98*(7^6+5-4^3^2+1)$
13839308	$(98*7+6)*(5^4*32-1)$	14160118	$-98*(7^6+5-4^3^2-1)$
13840692	$(98*7+6)*(5^4*32+1)$	14160902	$-98*(7^6-5-4^3^2+1)$
13898304	$9/8*(7^6*5+43)*21$	14161098	$-98*(7^6-5-4^3^2-1)$
13905368	$9*(-8+(7-6*5^4/3)^2)-1$	14220368	$9*(-8+(7+6*5^4/3)^2)-1$
13905370	$9*(-8+(7-6*5^4/3)^2)+1$	14220370	$9*(-8+(7+6*5^4/3)^2)+1$
13905512	$9*(8+(7-6*5^4/3)^2)-1$	14220512	$9*(8+(7+6*5^4/3)^2)-1$
13905514	$9*(8+(7-6*5^4/3)^2)+1$	14220514	$9*(8+(7+6*5^4/3)^2)+1$
13961276	$98*7^6*(5^4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	14340365	$9^8-7^6*(5*(4+3)^2-1)$
13968724	$98*7^6*(5^4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	14411292	$98*((7^6-5)/4*(3+2)-1)$
13999585	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)*(4+3)-2-1)$	14411488	$98*((7^6-5)/4*(3+2)+1)$
13999619	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)*(4+3)+2+1)$	14412517	$98*((7^6+5)/4*(3+2)-1)$
13999653	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)*(4+3)+2-1)$	14412713	$98*((7^6+5)/4*(3+2)+1)$
14000329	$98-7^6*(5-4*(32-1))$	14444064	$9*8*(-7-6+5^4*321)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
14444916	$9*8*(-7/6+5^4*321)$	15059188	$(9+(8*7^6+5)*4)*(3+2-1)$
14444928	$9*8*(-7+6+5^4*321)$	15119244	$9*(8+76)*(5^4*32-1)$
14445072	$9*8*(7-6+5^4*321)$	15120756	$9*(8+76)*(5^4*32+1)$
14445084	$9*8*(7/6+5^4*321)$	15175782	$(-98+(7^6-5)*43)*(2+1)$
14445936	$9*8*(7+6+5^4*321)$	15176061	$9-(8-(7^6-5)*43)*(2+1)$
14456596	$(9+8)*(7^6*5+4^3*2-1)$	15176091	$-9+(8+(7^6-5)*43)*(2+1)$
14456630	$(9+8)*(7^6*5+4^3*2+1)$	15176109	$9+(8+(7^6-5)*43)*(2+1)$
14522833	$(9+8*(7-6/5))*(4^3*2+1)$	15176370	$(98+(7^6-5)*43)*(2+1)$
14548919	$9*(-8+(7/6+5)*4^3*2-1)$	15176623	$-98+7^6*(5+4*(32-1))$
14548921	$9*(-8+(7/6+5)*4^3*2+1)$	15176819	$98+7^6*(5+4*(32-1))$
14549063	$9*(8+(7/6+5)*4^3*2-1)$	15177072	$(-98+(7^6+5)*43)*(2+1)$
14549065	$9*(8+(7/6+5)*4^3*2+1)$	15177351	$9-(8-(7^6+5)*43)*(2+1)$
14550376	$(9/(8+(7*6)^5+4^3*2))^{\wedge}-1$	15177381	$-9+(8+(7^6+5)*43)*(2+1)$
14584818	$(-98+(7^6-5)*4)*(32-1)$	15177399	$9+(8+(7^6+5)*43)*(2+1)$
14586058	$(-98+(7^6+5)*4)*(32-1)$	15177660	$(98+(7^6+5)*43)*(2+1)$
14587617	$9-(8-(7^6-5)*4)*(32-1)$	15204196	$-98-(7-65)*(4^3*2-1)$
14587758	$-98+(7^6-5)*4*(32-1)$	15204253	$-98-(7-65)*4^3*2-1$
14587954	$98+(7^6-5)*4*(32-1)$	15204255	$-98-(7-65)*4^3*2+1$
14588485	$9-8*7^6*(5-43/2+1)$	15204449	$98-(7-65)*4^3*2-1$
14588998	$-98+(7^6+5)*4*(32-1)$	15204451	$98-(7-65)*4^3*2+1$
14589194	$98+(7^6+5)*4*(32-1)$	15204508	$98-(7-65)*(4^3*2+1)$
14589353	$9+(8+(7^6+5)*4)*(32-1)$	15291675	$(9+8*(7/6+5))*(4^3*2-1)$
14590894	$(98+(7^6-5)*4)*(32-1)$	15371398	$98*((7^6+5)*4/3-21)$
14592134	$(98+(7^6+5)*4)*(32-1)$	15373407	$98*((7^6+5)*4/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
14676377	$9-8*7*(65-4^3*2+1)$	15373505	$98*((7^6+5)*4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
14676423	$-9-8*(7*(65-4^3*2)-1)$	15375514	$98*((7^6+5)*4/3+21)$
14676425	$9-8*(7*(65-4^3*2)+1)$	15388352	$98*(7^6+5^4*3*21)$
14676441	$9-8*(7*(65-4^3*2)-1)$	15466487	$-9-8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*(4-3*21)$
14676489	$9-8*7*(65-4^3*2-1)$	15466505	$9-8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*(4-3*21)$
14683657	$9+8*7*(65+4^3*2-1)$	15525774	$(-98+(7^6-5)*4)*(32+1)$
14683687	$-9+8*(7*(65+4^3*2)-1)$	15527094	$(-98+(7^6+5)*4)*(32+1)$
14683705	$9+8*(7*(65+4^3*2)-1)$	15528753	$9-(8-(7^6-5)*4)*(32+1)$
14683721	$9+8*(7*(65+4^3*2)+1)$	15528910	$-98+(7^6-5)*4*(32+1)$
14683751	$-9+8*7*(65+4^3*2+1)$	15529106	$98+(7^6-5)*4*(32+1)$
14683769	$9+8*7*(65+4^3*2+1)$	15530230	$-98+(7^6+5)*4*(32+1)$
14704325	$(9*8-7^6*5)*(4^3*2-1)$	15530426	$98+(7^6+5)*4*(32+1)$
14705700	$(-9-8+7^6*5)*(4^3*2+1)$	15530583	$-9+(8+(7^6+5)*4)*(32+1)$
14705925	$9*(-8+7^6*5)*((4/3)^2+1)$	15530601	$9+(8+(7^6+5)*4)*(32+1)$
14706100	$(-9+8+7^6*5)*(4^3*2+1)$	15532242	$(98+(7^6-5)*4)*(32+1)$
14706150	$(9-8+7^6*5)*(4^3*2+1)$	15533562	$(98+(7^6+5)*4)*(32+1)$
14706550	$(9+8+7^6*5)*(4^3*2+1)$	15539223	$(9*87-6)*(5^4*32-1)$
14707925	$(9*8+7^6*5)*(4^3*2+1)$	15540777	$(9*87-6)*(5^4*32+1)$
14758848	$9*876*(5^4*3-2-1)$	15655293	$9*(87*(-6+5^4*32)-1)$
14766723	$9*(876*(5^4*3-2)-1)$	15655311	$9*(87*(-6+5^4*32)+1)$
14766731	$9*876*(5^4*3-2)-1$	15664689	$9*(87*(6+5^4*32)-1)$
14766732	$9*876*(5^4*3-2)^{\wedge}1$	15664707	$9*(87*(6+5^4*32)+1)$
14766733	$9*876*(5^4*3-2)+1$	15711990	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-43^{\wedge}2-1)$
14766741	$9*(876*(5^4*3-2)+1)$	15712008	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-43^{\wedge}2+1)$
14774616	$9*876*(5^4*3-2+1)$	15716544	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-4^3*21)$
14778558	$9*876*(5^4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	15717084	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-4^3*21)$
14786442	$9*876*(5^4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	15720513	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-43*21)$
14790384	$9*876*(5^4*3+2-1)$	15724743	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-432-1)$
14798259	$9*(876*(5^4*3+2)-1)$	15724751	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-432)-1$
14798267	$9*876*(5^4*3+2)-1$	15724753	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-432)+1$
14798268	$9*876*(5^4*3+2)^{\wedge}1$	15724761	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-432+1)$
14798269	$9*876*(5^4*3+2)+1$	15725715	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-4-321)$
14798277	$9*(876*(5^4*3+2)+1)$	15725787	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)+4-321)$
14806152	$9*876*(5^4*3+2+1)$	15728232	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-43)-21$
14810961	$9^{\wedge}8-7^6*5*((4+3)^2-1)$	15728274	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-43)+21$
14823135	$-9+8*(7^6-5)/4^3*21$	15728283	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-4)-321$
14823153	$9+8*(7^6-5)/4^3*21$	15728351	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-4^3/2)-1$
14823615	$9-(8-7^6*(5+4-3))^*21$	15728353	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-4^3/2)+1$
14823933	$-9+(8+7^6*(5+4-3))^*21$	15728355	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)+4)-321$
14823951	$9+(8+7^6*(5+4-3))^*21$	15728463	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)+4/3-21)$
14824413	$9+8*(7^6+5)/4^3*21$	15728567	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1$
14825832	$(98+7^6*(5+4-3))^*21$	15728713	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)+4^{\wedge}(3/2))+1$
14941325	$-98-7^6*(5-4*(32+1))$	15728841	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)+4/3+21)$
14941521	$98-7^6*(5-4*(32+1))$	15728925	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-4)+321$
15013077	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)-43^{\wedge}(2+1))$	15728927	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)+4^3/2)-1$
15058956	$(-9+(8*7^6-5)*4)*(3+2-1)$	15728929	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)+4^3/2)+1$
15059028	$(9+(8*7^6-5)*4)*(3+2-1)$	15728997	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)+4)+321$
15059116	$(-9+(8*7^6+5)*4)*(3+2-1)$	15729006	$9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)+43)-21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
15729048	$9^*(8^7/(6/5)+43)+21$	16510968	$-9^*(8+7*(65-4^3\wedge 2-1))$
15731493	$9^*(8^7/(6/5)-4+321)$	16513109	$-9^*(8+7*(6^5-4^3\wedge 2))-1$
15731565	$9^*(8^7/(6/5)+4+321)$	16513111	$-9^*(8+7*(6^5-4^3\wedge 2))+1$
15732519	$9^*(8^7/(6/5)+432-1)$	16513253	$9^*(8-7*(6^5-4^3\wedge 2))-1$
15732527	$9^*(8^7/(6/5)+432)-1$	16513255	$9^*(8-7*(6^5-4^3\wedge 2))+1$
15732529	$9^*(8^7/(6/5)+432)+1$	16514306	$-9^*(8+7*(6+5-4^3\wedge 2))-1$
15732537	$9^*(8^7/(6/5)+432+1)$	16514308	$-9^*(8+7*(6+5-4^3\wedge 2))+1$
15736767	$9^*(8^7/(6/5)+43^*21)$	16514478	$9^*(8^7-65-4^3\wedge 2-1)$
15740196	$9^*(8^7/(6/5)+4^*321)$	16514496	$9^*(8^7-65-4^3\wedge 2+1)$
15740736	$9^*(8^7/(6/5)+4^3\wedge 21)$	16514936	$-9^*(8+7*(6-5-4^3\wedge 2))-1$
15745272	$9^*(8^7/(6/5)+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	16514938	$-9^*(8+7*(6-5-4^3\wedge 2))+1$
15745290	$9^*(8^7/(6/5)+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	16514999	$-9^*(8-7*(6-5)^*4^3\wedge 2)-1$
15752863	$-98+(7/(6/54))^(3+2-1)$	16515001	$-9^*(8-7*(6-5)^*4^3\wedge 2)+1$
15753059	$98+(7/(6/54))^(3+2-1)$	16515053	$9^*(8^7(7-6+5)^*(4+3)-2)-1$
15764975	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6^*(5/4+3-21)$	16515055	$9^*(8^7(7-6+5)^*(4+3)-2)+1$
15779211	$(9^*87+6)^*(5^4\wedge 32-1)$	16515089	$9^*(8^7(7-6+5)^*(4+3)+2)-1$
15780789	$(9^*87+6)^*(5^4\wedge 32+1)$	16515091	$9^*(8^7(7-6+5)^*(4+3)+2)+1$
15848901	$(9^*8+7)^*(-6+5^4\wedge 321)$	16515143	$9^*(8+7*(6-5)^*4^3\wedge 2)-1$
15849849	$(9^*8+7)^*(6+5^4\wedge 321)$	16515206	$9^*(8+7*(6-5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$
15879969	$(98-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*(4-32+1)$	16515208	$9^*(8+7*(6-5+4^3\wedge 2))+1$
15881382	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6^*5-43)^*(2+1))$	16515648	$9^*(8^7+65-4^3\wedge 2-1)$
15882246	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4)^*3-21)$	16515666	$9^*(8^7+65-4^3\wedge 2+1)$
15882370	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6^*54)^*(3/2+1)$	16515692	$-9^*(8-7*(6+5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$
15882517	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^*54^*(3/2+1)$	16515694	$-9^*(8-7*(6+5+4^3\wedge 2))+1$
15882604	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6^*54)^*(3/2+1)$	16515836	$9^*(8+7*(6+5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$
15882644	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*54)^*(3/2+1)$	16515838	$9^*(8+7*(6+5+4^3\wedge 2))+1$
15882713	$98+7^{\wedge}6^*54^*(3/2+1)$	16516889	$-9^*(8-7*(6^5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$
15882860	$(98+7^{\wedge}6^*54)^*(3/2+1)$	16516891	$-9^*(8-7*(6^5+4^3\wedge 2))+1$
15883128	$9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6^*5+4)^*3+21)$	16517033	$9^*(8+7*(6^5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$
15885261	$(98+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*(-4+32-1)$	16519032	$-9^*(8-7*(65+4^3\wedge 2-1))$
15924033	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)^*(-5+4^{\wedge}(3^2-1))$	16519086	$-9^*(8-7*(65+4^3\wedge 2)+1)$
15926463	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^2-1))$	16519104	$-9^*(8-7*(65+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$
15953629	$(9+8/7)^*(6^*(5+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	16519158	$-9^*(8-7*(65+4^3\wedge 2+1))$
15999465	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3)^*2-1$	16519302	$9^*(8+7*(65+4^3\wedge 2+1))$
15999567	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	16530612	$9^*8^{\wedge}7-6^*(5^4\wedge(3/2)+1)$
15999601	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	16530624	$9^*8^{\wedge}7-6^*(5^4\wedge(3/2)-1)$
15999669	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3)^*2-1$	16675965	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*3^*21)$
15999703	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3)^*2+1$	16676109	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*3^*21)$
16000105	$9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*4-3)-21)$	16706060	$-98-7^{\wedge}6^*(5-(4+3)^*21)$
16000441	$9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*4-3)+21)$	16706256	$98-7^{\wedge}6^*(5-(4+3)^*21)$
16000825	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3)^*2-1$	16739163	$9^*(87+6)^*(5^4\wedge 32-1)$
16000859	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3)^*2+1$	16739712	$9-(8/7-65)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
16000927	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	16740837	$9^*(87+6)^*(5^4\wedge 32+1)$
16000961	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	16822994	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
16001063	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3)^*2+1$	16823020	$-9^*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
16025111	$-9^*(8+7*(6^5-4^3\wedge 2))-1$	16823164	$9^*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
16025113	$-9^*(8+7*(6^5-4^3\wedge 2))+1$	16823190	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
16025255	$9^*(8-7*(6^5-4^3\wedge 2))-1$	16824424	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
16025257	$9^*(8-7*(6^5-4^3\wedge 2))+1$	16824450	$-9^*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
16117815	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4^*(32+1))$	16824594	$9^*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
16118011	$98+7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4^*(32+1))$	16824620	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
16122102	$9^*(8-7/6)^*(5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	16851447	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^4)^*(3-21)$
16134648	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4^3/21)$	16851465	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^4)^*(3-21)$
16134792	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4^3/21)$	16863192	$9^*8^*((7^{\wedge}6-543)^*2-1)$
16261708	$(9/((8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5^4-3))^*2))^{\wedge}-1$	16863255	$9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-543)^*2-1)$
16406110	$-98+7^*6^*(5^4\wedge(3/2)-1)$	16863273	$9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-543)^*2+1)$
16406145	$-98+7^*(6^5\wedge 4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	16863336	$9^*8^*((7^{\wedge}6-543)^*2+1)$
16406159	$-98+7^*(6^5\wedge 4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	16930197	$-9-(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5^4)^*(3-21)$
16406194	$-98+7^*6^*(5^4\wedge(3/2)+1)$	16930215	$9-(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5^4)^*(3-21)$
16406306	$98+7^*6^*(5^4\wedge(3/2)-1)$	16931673	$9^*((8^*7^{\wedge}6-543)^*2-1)$
16406341	$98+7^*(6^5\wedge 4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	16931691	$9^*((8^*7^{\wedge}6-543)^*2+1)$
16406355	$98+7^*(6^5\wedge 4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	16933239	$9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54-3)^*2-1)$
16406390	$98+7^*6^*(5^4\wedge(3/2)+1)$	16933257	$9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54-3)^*2+1)$
16444203	$9^*(8^7/(6/5)+4^3\wedge(2+1))$	16933617	$9^*((8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54)-3)^*2-1)$
16468802	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4/3)^*21$	16933635	$9^*((8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54)-3)^*2+1)$
16470701	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4/3)^*21$	16933671	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(3-21)$
16471019	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4/3)^*21$	16933689	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(3-21)$
16471037	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4/3)^*21$	16933725	$9^*((8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54)+3)^*2-1)$
16472918	$(98+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4/3)^*21$	16933743	$9^*((8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54)+3)^*2+1)$
16510842	$-9^*(8+7*(65-4^3\wedge 2+1))$	16934103	$9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54+3)^*2-1)$
16510896	$-9^*(8+7*(65-4^3\wedge 2)+1)$	16934121	$9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54+3)^*2+1)$
16510914	$-9^*(8+7*(65-4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	16934535	$9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5-43)^*2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
16934553	$9*(8*(7^6-5-43)*2+1)$	17039521	$9+87+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
16935975	$9*(8*(7^6+5-43)*2-1)$	17039523	$98+(7+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
16935993	$9*(8*(7^6+5-43)*2+1)$	17039530	$98+7+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
16938585	$9-8*(7^6-5*4)*(3-21)$	17039981	$98*7+65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
16938855	$9*(8*(7^6-54/3)*2-1)$	17040078	$9*87+65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
16938873	$9*(8*(7^6-54/3)*2+1)$	17040111	$98*7+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
16939953	$9*((8*(7^6-5)-43)*2-1)$	17040208	$9*87+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
16939971	$9*((8*(7^6-5)-43)*2+1)$	17056263	$(98-7^6*5)*(4-32-1)$
16940169	$9-8*(7^6-5-4)*(3-21)$	17058282	$-98+(7^6-5)*((4*3)\wedge 2+1)$
16940493	$9-(8*(7^6+54)*3-21)$	17058308	$-9*8+(7^6-5)*((4*3)\wedge 2+1)$
16940673	$9-(8*(7^6-5)-4)*(3-21)$	17058452	$9*8+(7^6-5)*((4*3)\wedge 2+1)$
16941162	$(-98+7^6*(5+43))*(2+1)$	17058478	$98+(7^6-5)*((4*3)\wedge 2+1)$
16941750	$(98+7^6*(5+43))*(2+1)$	17058882	$9+(8-7^6*5)*(4-32-1)$
16942113	$9-(8*(7^6+5)-4)*(3-21)$	17059346	$9-(8+7^6*5)*(4-32-1)$
16942257	$9-(8*(7^6+5)+4)*(3-21)$	17059732	$-98+(7^6+5)*((4*3)\wedge 2+1)$
16942419	$-9-(8*7^6+54)*(3-21)$	17059758	$-9*8+(7^6+5)*((4*3)\wedge 2+1)$
16942437	$9-(8*7^6+54)*(3-21)$	17059902	$9*8+(7^6+5)*((4*3)\wedge 2+1)$
16942761	$9-8*(7^6+5+4)*(3-21)$	17059928	$98+(7^6+5)*((4*3)\wedge 2+1)$
16942941	$9*((8*(7^6+5)+43)*2-1)$	17061947	$(98+7^6*5)*(-4+32+1)$
16942959	$9*((8*(7^6+5)+43)*2+1)$	17068689	$9*(8^7-6-5^4*321)$
16944039	$9*(8*(7^6+54/3)*2-1)$	17068797	$9*(8^7+6-5^4*321)$
16944057	$9*(8*(7^6+54/3)*2+1)$	17202430	$98*((7^6-5^4)*3/2-1)$
16944345	$9-8*(7^6+5*4)*(3-21)$	17202626	$98*((7^6-5^4)*3/2+1)$
16946919	$9*(8*(7^6-5+43)*2-1)$	17218601	$((9^8-7+6)/5-43)*2-1$
16946937	$9*(8*(7^6-5+43)*2+1)$	17218773	$((9^8-7+6)/5+43)*2-1$
16948359	$9*(8*(7^6+5+43)*2-1)$	17218775	$((9^8-7+6)/5+43)*2+1$
16948377	$9*(8*(7^6+5+43)*2+1)$	17265661	$((9^8+7^6)/5-43)*2-1$
16948791	$9*(8*(7^6+54-3)*2-1)$	17265663	$((9^8+7^6)/5-43)*2+1$
16948809	$9*(8*(7^6+54-3)*2+1)$	17265833	$((9^8+7^6)/5+43)*2-1$
16949169	$9*((8*(7^6+54)-3)*2-1)$	17265835	$((9^8+7^6)/5+43)*2+1$
16949187	$9*((8*(7^6+54)-3)*2+1)$	17286367	$98*((7^6-54)*3/2-1)$
16949223	$-9-8*(7^6+54)*(3-21)$	17286563	$98*((7^6-54)*3/2+1)$
16949277	$9*((8*(7^6+54)+3)*2-1)$	17291365	$98*((7^6-5^4)*3/2-1)$
16949295	$9*((8*(7^6+54)+3)*2+1)$	17291561	$98*((7^6-5^4)*3/2+1)$
16949655	$9*(8*(7^6+54+3)*2-1)$	17291610	$(-98+(7^6-5)*4+3)*21$
16949673	$9*(8*(7^6+54+3)*2+1)$	17293509	$9-(8-(7^6-5)*4+3)*21$
16951221	$9*(8*(7^6+54+3)*2-1)$	17293827	$-9+(8+(7^6-5)*4+3)*21$
16951239	$9*(8*(7^6+54+3)*2+1)$	17293845	$9+(8+(7^6-5)*4+3)*21$
16952697	$-9-(8*7^6+5^4)*(3-21)$	17294979	$9-(8-(7^6+5)*4+3)*21$
16952715	$9-(8*7^6+5^4)*(3-21)$	17295297	$-9+(8+(7^6+5)*4+3)*21$
17004887	$-9*(8-7*(6^5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$	17295315	$9+(8+(7^6+5)*4+3)*21$
17004889	$-9*(8-7*(6^5+4^3\wedge 2))+1$	17297196	$(98+(7^6+5)*4+3)*21$
17005031	$9*(8+7*(6^5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$	17297245	$98*((7^6+5^4)*3/2-1)$
17005033	$9*(8+7*(6^5+4^3\wedge 2))+1$	17297441	$98*((7^6+5^4)*3/2+1)$
17019576	$9*8*((7^6+543)*2-1)$	17301579	$9+(8-7+65)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
17019639	$9*(8*(7^6+543)*2-1)$	17302243	$98*((7^6+54)*3/2-1)$
17019657	$9*(8*(7^6+543)*2+1)$	17302439	$98*((7^6+54)*3/2+1)$
17019720	$9*8*((7^6+543)*2+1)$	17386180	$98*((7^6+5^4)*3/2-1)$
17031447	$-9-8*(7^6+5^4)*(3-21)$	17386376	$98*((7^6+5^4)*3/2+1)$
17031465	$9-8*(7^6+5^4)*(3-21)$	17411954	$-98+7^6*(5+(4*3)\wedge 2-1)$
17038512	$-9*87+65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	17411980	$-9*8+7^6*(5+(4*3)\wedge 2-1)$
17038609	$-98*7+65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	17412124	$9*8+7^6*(5+(4*3)\wedge 2-1)$
17038642	$-9*87+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	17412150	$98+7^6*(5+(4*3)\wedge 2-1)$
17038739	$-98*7+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	17563589	$9*(8^7-6)-5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
17039190	$-98-7+65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	17563599	$9*(8^7-6)-5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
17039199	$-9-87+65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	17563697	$9*(8^7+6)-5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
17039204	$-98+7+65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	17563707	$9*(8^7+6)-5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
17039223	$-9*8+(7+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	17577333	$9*(-87+(6-5+4)^3\wedge 2-1)$
17039249	$-98+(7+6)*(5*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	17577351	$9*(-87+(6-5+4)^3\wedge 2+1)$
17039309	$98/7+65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	17577620	$9*(-8*7+(6-5+4)^3\wedge 2)-1$
17039320	$-98-7+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	17577989	$9*(-8-7+(6-5+4)^3\wedge 2)-1$
17039327	$-98+(7+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	17577991	$9*(-8-7+(6-5+4)^3\wedge 2)+1$
17039329	$-9-87+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	17578628	$9*(8*7+(6-5+4)^3\wedge 2)-1$
17039334	$-98+7+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	17578630	$9*(8*7+(6-5+4)^3\wedge 2)+1$
17039386	$98-7+65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	17647252	$-98+7^6*(5+(4*3)\wedge 2+1)$
17039391	$9+87+65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	17647277	$9*(-8+7^6*5*(4/3+2))-1$
17039393	$98+(7+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	17647279	$9*(-8+7^6*5*(4/3+2))+1$
17039400	$98+7+65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	17647421	$9*(8+7^6*5*(4/3+2))-1$
17039411	$-98/7+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	17647423	$9*(8+7^6*5*(4/3+2))+1$
17039445	$9*8+(7+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	17647448	$98+7^6*(5+(4*3)\wedge 2+1)$
17039471	$98+(7+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	17794314	$9*(8^7-6*(5^4*32+1))$
17039516	$98-7+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	17794359	$9*(8^7-6*5^4*32-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
17794377	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6^*5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	18235958	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^*(32-1)$
17794422	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6^*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1))$	18235976	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^*(32-1)$
17825393	$9+(8-76)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	18279587	$9^{\wedge}8-7^*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
17825529	$9+(8-76)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	18279601	$9^{\wedge}8-7^*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
17826073	$9-(8-76)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	18353172	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3-21))$
17826191	$-9-(8-76)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	18353316	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3-21))$
17826209	$9-(8-76)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	18359046	$(9-8^*7)^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
17882550	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4+3)^*21)$	18359140	$(9-8^*7)^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
17882621	$(-9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4/3))^*(2+1)$	18359610	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
17882675	$(9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4/3))^*(2+1)$	18359704	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
17882746	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4+3)^*21)$	18421023	$-9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$
17904655	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	18421041	$9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$
17904689	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	18460918	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
17994840	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-321)$	18460920	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
17997220	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^*4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	18482337	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*((5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
17997254	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^*4)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	18505918	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
17998903	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	18505920	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
17998937	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	18510020	$9-(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4/3-21)$
17999515	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3+2)-1)$	18510887	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4/3-21)$
17999549	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3+2)+1)$	18510905	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4/3-21)$
18000036	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4-3)-21)$	18518859	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^*21)$
18000127	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	18519939	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6-5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
18000161	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	18520047	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
18000178	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3^*2-1)$	18521127	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^*21)$
18000199	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)^*(2+1)$	18559794	$9^*8^{\wedge}7-6/5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
18000206	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4-3)-2)-1$	18594587	$9^{\wedge}8-7^*((6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
18000208	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4-3)-2)+1$	18594601	$9^{\wedge}8-7^*((6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
18000229	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3-2+1)$	18673689	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6)-5^{\wedge}4*321$
18000242	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4-3)+2)-1$	18673737	$9^*8^{\wedge}7-6-5^{\wedge}4*321$
18000263	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3+2-1)$	18673749	$9^*8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}4*321$
18000282	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*(2+1)$	18673797	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6)-5^{\wedge}4*321$
18000312	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*(2+1)$	18683798	$(9+8^{\wedge}7)^*-6/((5/4-3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
18000331	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3-2+1)$	18688689	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6-5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$
18000352	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4-3)-2)+1$	18688797	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$
18000365	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3+2-1)$	18693378	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)^*(2+1)$
18000386	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4-3)+2)-1$	18694305	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6-5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$
18000388	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4-3)+2)+1$	18694323	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6-5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$
18000395	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)^*(2+1)$	18694413	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$
18000414	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4-3)+21)$	18694431	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$
18000416	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3^*2+1)$	18699939	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6-5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
18000433	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	18700047	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
18000467	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	18706289	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(54^*3-2-1)$
18000591	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*(2+1)$	18739314	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6-5^{\wedge}4*(3+21))$
18000756	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	18739422	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}4*(3+21))$
18001045	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3+2)-1)$	18755622	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$
18001079	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3+2)+1)$	18755730	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$
18001657	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	18756756	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
18001691	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	18756864	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
18003195	$9^*(8*(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21)$	18771984	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21))$
18003340	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^*4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	18772929	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*5^{\wedge}4*3-21)$
18003374	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^*4)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	18773009	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2))-1$
18003537	$9^*(8*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	18773011	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2))+1$
18003573	$9^*(8*(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21)$	18773225	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2))-1$
18005754	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+321)$	18773227	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2))+1$
18095905	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	18773307	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$
18095939	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	18806543	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)-1$
18117955	$9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5/4-3+21)$	18806545	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)+1$
18162216	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$	18806813	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)-1$
18165051	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$	18806815	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)+1$
18166185	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(6*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$	18806921	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(6*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)-1$
18169020	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$	18806923	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(6*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)+1$
18235232	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^*(32-1)$	18807191	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)-1$
18235373	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^*(32-1)$	18807193	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)+1$
18235480	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^*(32-1)$	18819216	$-9^*8^*(765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
18235497	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	18819279	$-9^*(8*(765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
18235523	$-9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	18819297	$-9^*(8*(765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
18235569	$98+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^*(32-1)$	18819360	$-9^*8^*(765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
18235621	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^*(32-1)$	18823512	$(9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4)^*(-3^{\wedge}2+1)$
18235667	$9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	18824168	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4)^*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
18235693	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	18833859	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21)$
18235728	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^*(32-1)$	18836127	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21)$
18235817	$98+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^*(32-1)$	18840509	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7-(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^*2)-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
18840511	$9*(8^7 - (6+5^4*3)^2)+1$	18958305	$9+8*7^6*(5^4+3/21)$
18840725	$9*(8^7+(6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	18975509	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4*3-2))-1$
18840727	$9*(8^7+(6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	18975511	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4*3-2))+1$
18841599	$-9*(8*(7*65-4^3^2)+1)$	18975725	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4*3+2))-1$
18841617	$-9*(8*(7*65-4^3^2)-1)$	18975727	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4*3+2))+1$
18846999	$-9*(8*(76*5-4^3^2)+1)$	18976752	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4*3+21))$
18847017	$-9*(8*(76*5-4^3^2)-1)$	18983646	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2-1)$
18851862	$9*8^7-6*(5^4*3^2+1)$	18984132	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2+1)$
18851874	$9*8^7-6*(5^4*3^2-1)$	18984618	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2-1)$
18857411	$9*(8^7-6*(5^4+3)/2)-1$	18985104	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2+1)$
18857413	$9*(8^7-6*(5^4+3)/2)+1$	18991872	$9*(8^7-6*(5^4-3)^2+1)$
18857573	$9*(8^7-6*(5^4-3)/2)-1$	18991980	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4-3)^2+1)$
18857575	$9*(8^7-6*(5^4-3)/2)+1$	18993006	$9*(8^7-6*(5^4+3)^2+1)$
18859247	$9*8*(7*6*5-4^3^2)-1$	18993114	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4+3)^2+1)$
18859249	$9*8*(7*6*5-4^3^2)+1$	19009314	$9*(8^7-6+5^4*(3+21))$
18861243	$9*8^7-6*5^4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	19009422	$9*(8^7+6+5^4*(3+21))$
18861984	$9*(8^7-6*(5^4/3+21))$	19048689	$9*(8^7-6+5^4*(32-1))$
18862929	$9*(8^7-6*5^4/3-21)$	19048797	$9*(8^7+6+5^4*(32-1))$
18864252	$9*(8^7-6*(5^4/3-21))$	19050318	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*(3-21))$
18864993	$9*8^7-6*5^4*(3/2+1)$	19050462	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4)*(3-21))$
18866838	$9*8^7-6*((5^4+3)^2-1)$	19054323	$9*(8^7-6+5^4*32+1)$
18866898	$9*8^7-6*((5^4-3)^2+1)$	19054413	$9*(8^7+6+5^4*32-1)$
18866910	$9*8^7-6*((5^4-3)^2-1)$	19054431	$9*(8^7+6+5^4*32+1)$
18870509	$9*(8^7-(6+5^4/3)^2)-1$	19055826	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*(3-21))$
18870725	$9*(8^7+(6-5^4/3)^2)-1$	19055970	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4)*(3-21))$
18870727	$9*(8^7+(6-5^4/3)^2)+1$	19057374	$(98-7^6*(5+4))*(3-21)$
18871814	$9*(8^7-6)-5^4*(3+2-1)$	19057608	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*(3-21))$
18871922	$9*(8^7+6)-5^4*(3+2-1)$	19058877	$9*(-8+7^6*5^4/3-21)$
18872736	$9*(8^7+6-5^4/3+21)$	19058904	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*(3-21))$
18876000	$9*(8^7-6+5^4/3-21)$	19059011	$9*(-8+(7^6*(5+4)-3)^2)-1$
18876814	$9*(8^7-6)+5^4*(3+2-1)$	19059013	$9*(-8+(7^6*(5+4)-3)^2)+1$
18876922	$9*(8^7+6)+5^4*(3+2-1)$	19059263	$9*(8+(7^6*(5+4)+3)^2)-1$
18878009	$9*(8^7-(6-5^4/3)^2)-1$	19059265	$9*(8+(7^6*(5+4)+3)^2)+1$
18878011	$9*(8^7-(6-5^4/3)^2)+1$	19059399	$9*(8+7^6*5^4/3+21)$
18878227	$9*(8^7+(6+5^4/3)^2)+1$	19060047	$9*(8^7+6+5^4*(32+1))$
18881826	$9*8^7+6*((5^4-3)^2-1)$	19060524	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*(3-21))$
18881838	$9*8^7+6*((5^4-3)^2+1)$	19060902	$(98+7^6*(5+4))*(3-21)$
18881898	$9*8^7+6*((5^4+3)^2-1)$	19062306	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*(3-21))$
18883743	$9*8^7+6*5^4*(3/2+1)$	19062450	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4)*(3-21))$
18884484	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4/3-21))$	19067814	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*(3-21))$
18886752	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4/3+21))$	19067958	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4)*(3-21))$
18887493	$9*8^7+6*5^4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	19074939	$9*(8^7-6)+5^4*321$
18889487	$9*8*(7*6*5+4^3^2)-1$	19074987	$9*8^7-6+5^4*321$
18889489	$9*8*(7*6*5+4^3^2)+1$	19074999	$9*8^7+6+5^4*321$
18891161	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4-3)/2)-1$	19075047	$9*(8^7+6)+5^4*321$
18891163	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4-3)/2)+1$	19092761	$9-8*7^6*(5/(4+3)-21)$
18891323	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4+3)/2)-1$	19160316	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*(3-21))$
18891325	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4+3)/2)+1$	19176689	$-98+7^6*(5^4*3+2-1)$
18896862	$9*8^7+6*(5^4*3^2-1)$	19176885	$98+7^6*(5^4*3+2-1)$
18896874	$9*8^7+6*(5^4*3^2+1)$	19188942	$9*8^7+6/5*(4^3^2+1)$
18908009	$9*(8^7-(6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	19214076	$98*((7^6*5+4)/3-21)$
18908011	$9*(8^7-(6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	19216085	$98*((7^6*5+4)/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
18908225	$9*(8^7+(6+5^4*3)^2)-1$	19216183	$98*((7^6*5+4)/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
18908227	$9*(8^7+(6+5^4*3)^2)+1$	19217408	$98*(7^6*5+43)/(2+1)$
18912609	$9*(8^7-(6-5^4/3)^2+1)$	19218192	$98*((7^6*5+4)/3+21)$
18914877	$9*(8^7+(6+5^4/3)^2+1)$	19227609	$9*(8^7-(6-5^4*3)^2+1)$
18929376	$9*8*(765+4^3^2-1)$	19228689	$9*(8^7-6+5^4*3^2+1)$
18929439	$9*(8*(765+4^3^2)-1)$	19228797	$9*(8^7+6+5^4*3^2+1)$
18929457	$9*(8*(765+4^3^2)+1)$	19229877	$9*(8^7+(6+5^4*3)^2+1)$
18929520	$9*8*(765+4^3^2+1)$	19242816	$9*(8^7+(6-5^4/3)^2)-1$
18941391	$-98+7^6*(5^4*3-2+1)$	19242818	$9*(8^7+(6-5^4/3)^2)+1$
18941543	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4-3)^2)-1$	19287816	$9*(8^7+(6+5^4/3)^2)-1$
18941545	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4-3)^2)+1$	19287818	$9*(8^7+(6+5^4/3)^2)+1$
18941587	$98+7^6*(5^4*3-2+1)$	19293607	$-9+8*(7^6-5^4)*(43/2-1)$
18941813	$9*(8^7+(6*5^4-3)^2)-1$	19293625	$9+8*(7^6-5^4)*(43/2-1)$
18941815	$9*(8^7+(6*5^4-3)^2)+1$	19295265	$9+8*(7^6+5^4)*(43/2-1)$
18941921	$9*(8^7+(6*5^4+3)^2)-1$	19411698	$9-(8-7^6*5^4)*(32+1)$
18941923	$9*(8^7+(6*5^4+3)^2)+1$	19411855	$-98+(7^6*5^4)*(32+1)$
18942191	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4+3)^2)-1$	19411962	$9-(8-7^6*5^4)*(32+1)$
18942193	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4+3)^2)+1$	19411987	$-98+7^6*5^4*(4^3+21)$
18957816	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*(3-21))$	19412051	$98+(7^6*5^4)*(32+1)$
18957960	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4)*(3-21))$	19412119	$-98+(7^6*5^4)*(32+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
19412183	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4*3+21)$	19763448	$-9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)-3)*21$
19412208	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*(32+1)$	19763466	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)-3)*21$
19412226	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*(32+1)$	19763865	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4*3)*21$
19412315	$98+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*(32+1)$	19763903	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4/3)*21$
19412472	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*(32+1)$	19763921	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4/3)*21$
19412490	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*(32+1)$	19763931	$-9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4*3)*21$
19450023	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	19763949	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4*3)*21$
19450041	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	19763959	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4/3)*21$
19473489	$9+8/7*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	19763977	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4/3)*21$
19579716	$9*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)*21)$	19764054	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4-3)*21$
19583685	$9*(8^{\wedge}7+(6*5^{\wedge}4+3)*21)$	19764155	$-9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4/3)*21$
19586520	$9*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)*21)$	19764165	$(-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4+3))*(2+1)$
19597023	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3)*21$	19764173	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4/3)*21$
19597041	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3)*21$	19764180	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4+3)*21$
19659519	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-3)*21$	19764204	$-9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4-3)*21$
19659537	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-3)*21$	19764211	$-9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4/3)*21$
19659960	$-9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)-3)*21$	19764219	$(9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4+3))*(2+1)$
19659978	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)-3)*21$	19764222	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4-3)*21$
19660086	$-9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)+3)*21$	19764229	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4/3)*21$
19660104	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)+3)*21$	19764306	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5*(4+3))*21$
19660527	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3)*21$	19764327	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4-3)*21$
19660545	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3)*21$	19764330	$-9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4+3)*21$
19711263	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19764348	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4+3)*21$
19711281	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19764369	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4-3)*21$
19725648	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	19764393	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4*3)*21$
19725666	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	19764407	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4/3)*21$
19728903	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19764411	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4*3)*21$
19728921	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19764425	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4/3)*21$
19730023	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	19764453	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4*3)*21$
19730041	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	19764474	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)*3)*21$
19735441	$(-9+8*7)*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	19764558	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4-3)*21$
19735535	$(-9+8*7)*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	19764645	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-54/3)*21$
19737807	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-54*3)*21$	19764663	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-54/3)*21$
19737825	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-54*3)*21$	19764705	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4-3)*21$
19753431	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19764729	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4-3)*21$
19753449	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19764747	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4-3)*21$
19755111	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19764768	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)-3)*21$
19755129	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19764810	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)-3)*21$
19755447	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-54-3)*21$	19764894	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+5-4*3)*21$
19755465	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-54-3)*21$	19764900	$(-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4+3))*(2+1)$
19755888	$-9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)-3)*21$	19764901	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4/3)*21$
19755906	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)-3)*21$	19764903	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/(4+3))*21$
19756014	$-9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)+3)*21$	19764908	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5-4/3)*21$
19756032	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)+3)*21$	19764921	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/(4+3))*21$
19756455	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-54+3)*21$	19764953	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4/3)*21$
19756473	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-54+3)*21$	19764954	$(9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4+3))*(2+1)$
19756959	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19764964	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5+4/3)*21$
19756977	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19764971	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4/3)*21$
19758303	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19764985	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-(5-4)/3)*21$
19758321	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19765048	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+(5-4)/3)*21$
19758639	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19765079	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+(5-4)/3)*21$
19758657	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19765097	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+(5-4)/3)*21$
19759161	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*(4+3))*21$	19765110	$(-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+3))*(2+1)$
19760505	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)*3)*21$	19765111	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4/3)*21$
19760508	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19765118	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+5-4/3)*21$
19760526	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19765143	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/(4+3))*21$
19760648	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	19765161	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/(4+3))*21$
19760666	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	19765164	$(9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+3))*(2+1)$
19761177	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4-3)*21$	19765174	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+5+4/3)*21$
19761618	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)-3)*21$	19765181	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+5*4/3)*21$
19761621	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-54*3)*21$	19765272	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)+3)*21$
19761639	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-54*3)*21$	19765296	$-9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4+3)*21$
19761744	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)+3)*21$	19765314	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)+3)*21$
19761999	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-54/3)*21$	19765335	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4+3)*21$
19762017	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-54/3)*21$	19765377	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4+3)*21$
19762185	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4+3)*21$	19765401	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+54/3)*21$
19762839	$-9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19765419	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+54/3)*21$
19762857	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19765608	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+(5+4)*3)*21$
19763007	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4-3)*21$	19765629	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)-4*3)*21$
19763025	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4-3)*21$	19765657	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4/3)*21$
19763280	$-9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19765671	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4*3)*21$
19763298	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	19765713	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4+3)*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
19765734	$9+(8*(7^6+5)-4-3)*21$	19869537	$9+8*(7^6+5^4-3)*21$
19765737	$-9+8*(7^6+5/4+3)*21$	19869868	$9^8-7^6*(5+4^3*(2+1))$
19765755	$9+8*(7^6+5/4+3)*21$	19869960	$-9+(8*(7^6+5^4)-3)*21$
19765776	$9+(8*7^6+5*(4+3))*21$	19869978	$9+(8*(7^6+5^4)-3)*21$
19765835	$-9+(8*(7^6+5)-4/3)*21$	19870086	$-9+(8*(7^6+5^4)+3)*21$
19765845	$(-9+8*(7^6+5)*(4+3))*(2+1)$	19870104	$9+(8*(7^6+5^4)+3)*21$
19765853	$9+(8*(7^6+5)-4/3)*21$	19870527	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4+3)*21$
19765860	$9+(8*(7^6+5)-4+3)*21$	19870545	$9+8*(7^6+5^4+3)*21$
19765899	$(9+8*(7^6+5)*(4+3))*(2+1)$	19922877	$9+(8^7-6-5)*(4^3^2-1)$
19765902	$9+(8*(7^6+5)+4-3)*21$	19933023	$-9+(8*7^6+(5*4)^3)*21$
19765909	$9+(8*(7^6+5)+4/3)*21$	19933041	$9+(8*7^6+(5*4)^3)*21$
19766010	$-9+(8*(7^6+5)+4+3)*21$	19954314	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4*3^2-1))$
19766028	$9+(8*(7^6+5)+4+3)*21$	19954422	$9*(8^7+6*(5^4*3^2+1))$
19766105	$9+8*(7^6+5+4/3)*21$	19984203	$9^8*7-65^4*(3-21)$
19766133	$9+(8*(7^6+5)+4^3)*21$	19998137	$(9+8)*((7^6*5-4^3)^2-1)$
19766161	$9+8*(7^6+5^4/3)*21$	19998171	$(9+8)*((7^6*5-4^3)^2+1)$
19766199	$-9+8*(7^6-5+4^3)*21$	19999463	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)*(4+3^2)-1)$
19766217	$9+8*(7^6-5+4^3)*21$	19999497	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)*(4+3^2)+1)$
19766301	$9+(8/7^6-6+5^4*3)*21$	19999939	$(9+8)*((7^6*5-4^3)^2+1)$
19766616	$9+(8*(7^6+5+4)+3)*21$	20000075	$(9+8)*((7^6*5-4-3)^2-1)$
19766766	$-9+(8*(7^6+5)+4^3)*21$	20000109	$(9+8)*((7^6*5-4-3)^2+1)$
19766784	$9+(8*(7^6+5)+4^3)*21$	20000313	$(9+8)*7^6*5*(4-3)^2-1$
19767057	$9+8*(7^6+5+4+3)*21$	20000347	$(9+8)*7^6*5*(4-3)^2+1$
19767207	$-9+(8*(7^6+5)+4^3)*21$	20000551	$(9+8)*((7^6*5+4+3)^2-1)$
19767225	$9+(8*(7^6+5)+4^3)*21$	20000585	$(9+8)*((7^6*5+4+3)^2+1)$
19767897	$9+8*(7^6+5^4-3)*21$	20000721	$(9+8)*((7^6*5+4^3)^2-1)$
19768047	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4/3)*21$	20000755	$(9+8)*((7^6*5+4^3)^2+1)$
19768065	$9+8*(7^6+5^4/3)*21$	20001163	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*(4+3^2)-1)$
19768338	$9+(8*(7^6+5^4)-3)*21$	20001197	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*(4+3^2)+1)$
19768425	$-9+(8*7^6+5^4*3)*21$	20002489	$(9+8)*((7^6*5+4^3)^2-1)$
19768443	$9+(8*7^6+5^4*3)*21$	20002523	$(9+8)*((7^6*5+4^3)^2+1)$
19768446	$-9+(8*(7^6+5^4)+3)*21$	20078653	$(-9+(8/7^6-6-5)/4^4-3)/(2+1)$
19768464	$9+(8*(7^6+5^4)+3)*21$	20078659	$(9+(8/7^6-6-5)/4^4-3)/(2+1)$
19768905	$9+8*(7^6+5^4+3)*21$	20079613	$(-9+8*(7^6+5)^4^3)/(2+1)$
19769398	$-9+(8*7^6+5^4/3)*21$	20079619	$(9+8*(7^6+5)^4^3)/(2+1)$
19769416	$9+(8*7^6+5^4/3)*21$	20080023	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)*21$
19769538	$-9+(8*7^6+5^4*3)*21$	20080041	$9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)*21$
19769556	$9+(8*7^6+5^4*3)*21$	20117685	$(-9+8*7^6*(5+4+3))^2(2+1)$
19769559	$-9+8*(7^6+(5+4)^3)*21$	20117881	$-9+8*7^6*(5+4+3)^2(2+1)$
19769577	$9+8*(7^6+(5+4)^3)*21$	20117952	$-9*((8+7^6*(5-4^3))/2-1)$
19770903	$-9+8*(7^6+5*(4+3))^2(2+1)$	20117964	$9-(8-7^6*(5+4+3))^2(2+1)$
19770921	$9+8*(7^6+5*(4+3))^2(2+1)$	20117994	$-9+(8+7^6*(5+4+3))^2(2+1)$
19771407	$-9+8*(7^6-5+4^3)*21$	20118006	$9*((8-7^6*(5-4^3))/2-1)$
19771425	$9+8*(7^6-5+4^3)*21$	20118012	$9+(8+7^6*(5+4+3))^2(2+1)$
19771743	$-9+(8*7^6+5^4^3)*21$	20118024	$9*((8-7^6*(5-4^3))/2+1)$
19771761	$9+(8*7^6+5^4^3)*21$	20118077	$9+8*7^6*(5+4+3)^2(2+1)$
19773087	$-9+8*(7^6+5+4^3)*21$	20118273	$(9+8*7^6*(5+4+3))^2(2+1)$
19773105	$9+8*(7^6+5+4^3)*21$	20154869	$-9*(8*(7-6^6(-5+4^3))+2)-1$
19773591	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4-3)*21$	20154871	$-9*(8*(7-6^6(-5+4^3))+2)+1$
19773609	$9+(8*(7^6+5^4-3)*21$	20154905	$-9*(8*(7-6^6(-5+4^3))-2)-1$
19774032	$-9+(8*(7^6+5^4)-3)*21$	20154907	$-9*(8*(7-6^6(-5+4^3))-2)+1$
19774050	$9+(8*(7^6+5^4)-3)*21$	20155877	$9*(8*(7+6^6(-5+4^3))-2)-1$
19774158	$-9+(8*(7^6+5^4)+3)*21$	20155879	$9*(8*(7+6^6(-5+4^3))-2)+1$
19774176	$9+(8*(7^6+5^4)+3)*21$	20155913	$9*(8*(7+6^6(-5+4^3))+2)-1$
19774599	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4+3)*21$	20155915	$9*(8*(7+6^6(-5+4^3))+2)+1$
19774617	$9+8*(7^6+5^4+3)*21$	20184983	$-9+8*7*((6+5)^4^3^2-1)$
19774935	$-9+8*(7^6-5+4^3)*21$	20185009	$-9+8*7*((6+5)^4^3^2-1)$
19774953	$9+8*(7^6-5+4^3)*21$	20185023	$-9+8*7*((6+5)^4^3^2+1)$
19776615	$-9+8*(7^6+5+4^3)*21$	20185029	$9*(8^7-6)+5*(4^3^2-1)$
19776633	$9+8*(7^6+5+4^3)*21$	20185039	$9*(8^7-6)+5*(4^3^2+1)$
19792239	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)*21$	20185067	$-9+8*7*(6+5)*(4^3^2+1)$
19792257	$9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)*21$	20185109	$9+8*7*(6+5)*(4^3^2-1)$
19800023	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4/3)*21$	20185137	$9*(8^7+6)+5*(4^3^2-1)$
19800041	$9+8*(7^6+5^4/3)*21$	20185147	$9*(8^7+6)+5*(4^3^2+1)$
19801143	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)*21$	20185153	$9*8+7*((6+5)^4^3^2-1)$
19801161	$9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)*21$	20185167	$9*8+7*((6+5)^4^3^2+1)$
19804398	$-9+(8*7^6+5^4*3)*21$	20185179	$9+8*7*((6+5)^4^3^2-1)$
19804416	$9+(8*7^6+5^4*3)*21$	20185193	$9+8*7*((6+5)^4^3^2+1)$
19810278	$(9+8/7)*((6-5+4)^3^2+1)$	20185263	$9+8*7*(6+5)*(4^3^2+1)$
19818783	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)*21$	20234751	$-9+8*((7^6-5)^4^3/2-1)$
19818801	$9+8*(7^6+5^4*3)*21$	20234769	$9+8*((7^6-5)^4^3/2-1)$
19869519	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4-3)*21$	20234785	$9+8*((7^6-5)^4^3/2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
20236489	$9+8*((7^6+5)*43/2-1)$	21177055	$9*((8+7^6*5)^4-3^2)+1$
20236505	$9+8*((7^6+5)*43/2+1)$	21177069	$9*(-8+7^6*5^4)+321$
20253786	$9^8*(7^6/54)^3-21$	21177161	$9*((8+7^6*5)^4+3^2)-1$
20253828	$9^8*(7^6/54)^3+21$	21177163	$9*((8+7^6*5)^4+3^2)+1$
20267207	$9*(8^7*7^6+5^4*3^2)-1$	21177213	$9*(8+7^6*5^4)+321$
20267209	$9*(8^7*7^6+5^4*3^2)+1$	21177387	$9*((8+7^6*5)^4+32-1)$
20282122	$(-9-8)*(7^6-5*(4^3*2-1))$	21177405	$9*((8+7^6*5)^4+32+1)$
20282190	$(-9-8)*(7^6-5^4*3^2+1)$	21178377	$9*(8^7*7^6+5^4+3)/2+1$
20282224	$(-9-8)*(7^6-5^4*3^2-1)$	21179421	$9*((-8+7^6*5)^4+321)$
20282292	$(-9-8)*(7^6-5*(4^3*2+1))$	21179637	$9*(-8+7^6*5^4+321)$
20420433	$9*(-8+7^6*5*(4-3/21))$	21179781	$9*(8+7^6*5^4+321)$
20437321	$9+8^7*7^6*(5/(4+3)+21)$	21179997	$9*((8+7^6*5)^4+321)$
20442084	$(9-87)*(65-4^3*2+1)$	21218112	$9*8^7+6*(5^4*3/2)-1$
20442240	$(9-87)*(65-4^3*2-1)$	21218124	$9*8^7+6*(5^4*(3/2)+1)$
20452224	$(-9+87)*(65+4^3*2-1)$	21233070	$9*(8^7-65+4^3*2-1)$
20452380	$(-9+87)*(65+4^3*2+1)$	21233088	$9*(8^7-65+4^3*2+1)$
20470854	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+43/(2+1)))$	21233187	$9-(87-6)*(5-4^3*2+1)$
20470998	$9*(8^7*7^6*(5+43/(2+1)))$	21233349	$9-(87-6)*(5-4^3*2-1)$
20479982	$(-9+(8^7*(-7/6)/5)^4)/(3/2-1)$	21233997	$9+(87-6)*(5+4^3*2-1)$
20480018	$(9+(8^7*(7/6)/5)^4)/(3/2-1)$	21234159	$9+(87-6)*(5+4^3*2+1)$
20588477	$-98+7^6*5*(4+32-1)$	21234240	$9*(8^7+65+4^3*2-1)$
20588673	$98+7^6*5*(4+32-1)$	21234258	$9*(8^7+65+4^3*2+1)$
20679939	$9*(8^7-6+5^4*321)$	21294445	$(-9*8+7^6*5^4)/2+1$
20680047	$9*(8^7+6+5^4*321)$	21294493	$(9*8+7^6*5^4)/2+1$
20705353	$9+8*(7^6-5)*(43-21)$	21324783	$(9+8)*((7/(6^5+4^3))^4-2-1)$
20706343	$9+(8^7*7^6+5)*(43-21)$	21324817	$(9+8)*((7/(6^5+4^3))^4-2+1)$
20707113	$9+8*(7^6+5)*(43-21)$	21328011	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4+3/21))$
20709306	$9+(8+76-5)*(4^3*2-1)$	21328155	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4+3/21))$
20709464	$9+(8+76-5)*(4^3*2+1)$	21412127	$9-8^7*7^6*(5/4-3-21)$
20723589	$9*(-8+(7^6-(5^4)^3)*21)$	21454470	$9^8*(7/6/(-5-4)^3+2^4-1)$
20723733	$9*(8+(7^6-(5^4)^3)*21)$	21479274	$-9*(8+7^6*(5/(4+3)-21))$
20822916	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*(4/3-21))$	21479418	$9*(8-7^6*(5/(4+3)-21))$
20823060	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*(4/3-21))$	21491106	$98*((7^6-(5^4)^3)^2-1)$
20823775	$-98-7^6*(5-4^3)*(2+1)$	21491302	$98*((7^6-(5^4)^3)^2+1)$
20823971	$98-7^6*(5-4^3)^2*(2+1)$	21502584	$9^8*(-76/54^3+2^4-1)$
20824686	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*(4/3-21))$	21516954	$9^8-7^6*(5^4*3+21)$
20824830	$9*(8-(7^6+5)*(4/3-21))$	21592251	$9^8*(7/6*(5+4)^3-3+2^4-1)$
20983440	$(9+8)*((7/(6^5+4-3))^4-2-1)$	21627210	$9*(8+7/6*(5+4^3*2-1))$
20983474	$(9+8)*((7/(6^5+4-3))^4-2+1)$	21647257	$9+8*(7^6*(5^4+3)-21)$
21020857	$9+8*(7^6+5)*(4/3+21)$	21647413	$(-9+8^7*7^6*(5+4^3))/2+1$
21025485	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4-3/21))$	21647419	$(9+8^7*7^6*(5+4^3))/2+1$
21025629	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4-3/21))$	21647593	$9+8*(7^6*(5^4+3)+21)$
21046358	$9^8+7^6*(5-4^3*(2+1))$	21705246	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)*(43/2-1))$
21059073	$-98+7^6*(5^4*3^2-1)$	21705390	$9*(8+(7^6-5)*(43/2-1))$
21059269	$98+7^6*(5^4*3^2-1)$	21707091	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)*(43/2-1))$
21092913	$-9*(87-6*(5^4*3/2)-1)$	21707235	$9*(8+(7^6+5)*(43/2-1))$
21092958	$-9*(87-6*5^4*(3/2)+1)$	21764768	$9*(-8+7^6*5*(4+3^2)-1)$
21092976	$-9*(87-6*5^4*(3/2)-1)$	21764770	$9*(-8+7^6*5*(4+3^2)+1)$
21093021	$-9*(87-6*(5^4*(3/2)+1))$	21764967	$-98+7^6*5*(4+32+1)$
21094479	$9*(87+6*(5^4*(3/2)-1))$	21765163	$98+7^6*5*(4+32+1)$
21094524	$9*(87+6*5^4*(3/2)-1)$	21881214	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4*3)^2+1)$
21094542	$9*(87+6*5^4*(3/2)+1)$	21881358	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4*3)^2+1)$
21094587	$9*(87+6*(5^4*(3/2)+1))$	21933063	$9*(-8+7^6*5*(4+3/21))$
21109023	$-9+8*(7^6+(5^4)^3)*21$	21977343	$9/(8*(7+6-5^4/3))^4-2-1$
21109041	$9+8*(7^6+(5^4)^3)*21$	21977345	$9/(8*(7+6-5^4/3))^4-2+1$
21173643	$9*((-8+7^6*5)^4-321)$	22000265	$-98-7^6*(5-4^3*(2+1))$
21173859	$9*(-8+7^6*5^4-321)$	22000291	$9*-8-7^6*(5-4^3*(2+1))$
21174003	$9*(8+7^6*5^4-321)$	22000435	$9*8-7^6*(5-4^3*(2+1))$
21174219	$9*((8+7^6*5)^4-321)$	22000461	$98-7^6*(5-4^3*(2+1))$
21176427	$9*(-8+7^6*5^4)-321$	22019601	$9-(8+76)*(5-4^3*2+1)$
21176477	$9*((-8+7^6*5)^4-3^2)-1$	22019662	$-98/(7*(6*(5-4^3*2)+1))$
21176479	$9*((-8+7^6*5)^4-3^2)+1$	22019690	$-98/(7*(6*(5-4^3*2)-1))$
21176571	$9*(8+7^6*5^4)-321$	22019769	$9-(8+76)*(5-4^3*2-1)$
21176585	$9*((-8+7^6*5)^4+3^2)-1$	22020441	$9+(8+76)*(5+4^3*2-1)$
21176587	$9*((-8+7^6*5)^4+3^2)+1$	22020609	$9+(8+76)*(5+4^3*2+1)$
21176695	$9*(-8+7^6*5^4-3^2)+1$	22041069	$-9+(8+7^6)*(5^4/3-21)$
21176769	$(-9-8+7^6*5^4*3)*(2+1)$	22041087	$9+(8+7^6)*(5^4/3-21)$
21176801	$9*(-8+7^6*5^4+3^2)-1$	22057938	$(98+7^6)*(5^4/3-21)$
21176839	$9*(8+7^6*5^4-3^2)+1$	22116897	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4*3)^2+1)$
21176871	$(9+8+7^6*5^4*3)*(2+1)$	22117041	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4*3)^2+1)$
21176945	$9*(8+7^6*5^4+3^2)-1$	22118031	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4*3)^2+1)$
21177053	$9*((8+7^6*5)^4-3^2)-1$	22118175	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4*3)^2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
22129920	$-9 \cdot 87^*(6^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	22239936	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4 + 3) * 21)$
22129938	$9 \cdot 87^*(6^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	22240692	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + (5 + 4) * 3) * 21)$
22130094	$-9 \cdot 87^*(6^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	22240836	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + (5 + 4) * 3) * 21)$
22130112	$9 \cdot 87^*(6^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	22242204	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*(4 + 3)) * 21)$
22175109	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	22242348	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*(4 + 3)) * 21)$
22175253	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	22242771	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$
22194954	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	22242915	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$
22195098	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	22244661	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$
22196214	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 / 3) * 21)$	22244805	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$
22196358	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 / 3) * 21)$	22245228	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * 21)$
22205115	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * 21)$	22245372	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21)$
22222548	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	22246362	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21)$
22222692	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	22246506	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21)$
22222848	$9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3) * (2 + 1))$	22246740	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$
22224438	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	22246884	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$
22224582	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	22248630	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$
22224816	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21)$	22248774	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$
22224960	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21)$	22266207	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * 21)$
22225950	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21)$	22266351	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * 21)$
22226094	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21)$	22274964	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 / 3) * 21)$
22226517	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	22275108	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 / 3) * 21)$
22226661	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	22276224	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$
22228407	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	22276368	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$
22228551	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	22281441	$(-9 - 8) * (7^*6 - 5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$
22228974	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*(4 + 3)) * 21)$	22281543	$(-9 - 8) * (7^*6 - 5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
22229118	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*(4 + 3)) * 21)$	22281611	$(-9 - 8) * (7^*6 - 5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1))$
22230486	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - (5 + 4) * 3) * 21)$	22282869	$(9 + 8) * (7^*6 + 5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$
22231242	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4 - 3) * 21)$	22282937	$(9 + 8) * (7^*6 + 5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
22232187	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 / 3) * 21)$	22282971	$(9 + 8) * (7^*6 + 5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
22232331	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 / 3) * 21)$	22283039	$(9 + 8) * (7^*6 + 5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1))$
22232376	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4 + 3) * 21)$	22296069	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$
22233321	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4 - 3) * 21)$	22296213	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$
22233465	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4 - 3) * 21)$	22353147	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21)$
22234266	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	22353291	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21)$
22234329	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4 / 3) * 21)$	22354281	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21)$
22234392	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4 / 3) * 21)$	22354425	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21)$
22234455	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4 + 3) * 21)$	22468599	$-9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (3 + 21)$
22234473	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4 / 3) * 21)$	22468617	$9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (3 + 21)$
22234536	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4 / 3) * 21)$	22492050	$9 + (87 - 6 / 5) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
22234599	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4 + 3) * 21)$	22573599	$-9 + (8^*7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (3 + 21)$
22234833	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4 - 3) * 21)$	22573617	$9 + (8^*7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (3 + 21)$
22234896	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4 / 3) * 21)$	22578231	$-9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (3 + 21)$
22235040	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4 / 3) * 21)$	22578249	$9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (3 + 21)$
22235211	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4 - 3) * 21)$	22584777	$9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4) * (3 + 21)$
22235318	$(-98 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	22586871	$-9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * (3 + 21)$
22235439	$9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) + 3) * 21$	22586889	$9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * (3 + 21)$
22235500	$-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) - 3) * 21$	22587303	$-9 + (8^*7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (3 + 21)$
22235565	$9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) - 3) * 21$	22587321	$9 + (8^*7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (3 + 21)$
22235626	$-98 + (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) + 3) * 21$	22587543	$-9 + (8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5) - 4) * (3 + 21)$
22235642	$9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	22587561	$9 + (8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5) - 4) * (3 + 21)$
22235680	$-9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	22587735	$-9 + (8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5) + 4) * (3 + 21)$
22235696	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) - 3) * 21$	22587753	$9 + (8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5) + 4) * (3 + 21)$
22235698	$9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	22588137	$9 + (8^*7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4) * (3 + 21)$
22235757	$-9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) - 3) * 21$	22588359	$-9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5 / 4) * (3 + 21)$
22235775	$9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) - 3) * 21$	22588377	$9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5 / 4) * (3 + 21)$
22235822	$98 + (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) + 3) * 21$	22588407	$-9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * (3 + 21)$
22235883	$-9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) + 3) * 21$	22588641	$9 + (8^*7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * (3 + 21)$
22235901	$9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) + 3) * 21$	22588809	$9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * (3 + 21)$
22235967	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4 + 3) * 21)$	22588833	$9 + (8^*7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * (3 + 21)$
22236004	$(98 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	22588839	$-9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5 / 4) * (3 + 21)$
22236282	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4 / 3) * 21)$	22588857	$9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5 / 4) * (3 + 21)$
22236345	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4 + 3) * 21)$	22589097	$9 + (8^*7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4) * (3 + 21)$
22236723	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4 - 3) * 21)$	22589481	$9 + (8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5) - 4) * (3 + 21)$
22236786	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4 / 3) * 21)$	22589655	$-9 + (8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5) + 4) * (3 + 21)$
22236849	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4 / 3) * 21)$	22589673	$9 + (8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5) + 4) * (3 + 21)$
22236912	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4^*3) * 21)$	22589895	$-9 + (8^*7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4) * (3 + 21)$
22236930	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4 / 3) * 21)$	22589913	$9 + (8^*7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4) * (3 + 21)$
22237056	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4^*3) * 21)$	22589964	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * 21)$
22237857	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4 + 3) * 21)$	22590108	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * 21)$
22238802	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4 - 3) * 21)$	22590345	$9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * (3 + 21)$
22238991	$9^*(-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 / 3) * 21)$	22592439	$-9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4) * (3 + 21)$
22239135	$9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 / 3) * 21)$	22592457	$9 + 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4) * (3 + 21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
22598967	$-9+8*(7^6+54)*(3+21)$	23058763	$98*((7^6+5/4-3)*2-1)$
22598985	$9+8*(7^6+54)*(3+21)$	23059155	$98*(7^6*(-5+4+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$
22603599	$-9+(8*7^6+5^4)*(3+21)$	23059162	$98*((7^6-5/(4+3))*2+1)$
22603617	$9+(8*7^6+5^4)*(3+21)$	23059246	$98*((7^6+5/(4+3))*2-1)$
22691606	$98*((7^6-5^4*3)*2-1)$	23059253	$98*(7^6*(-5+4+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$
22691802	$98*((7^6-5^4*3)*2+1)$	23060674	$98*((7^6-5+4*3)*2+1)$
22708599	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4)*(3+21)$	23061262	$-98*(7^6*(5-4-3)-21)$
22708617	$9+8*(7^6+5^4)*(3+21)$	23062830	$98*((7^6+54/3)*2+1)$
22764033	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4/2-1)$	23064594	$98*((7^6+(5+4)*3)*2+1)$
22764051	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4/2+1)$	23066162	$98*((7^6+5*(4+3))*2+1)$
22764087	$9*((-8+(7^6-5)^4/2)/2+1)$	23066554	$98*((7^6-5+43)*2-1)$
22764141	$9*((8+(7^6-5)^4/2)-1)$	23066750	$98*((7^6-5+43)*2+1)$
22764159	$9*((8+(7^6-5)^4/2)+1)$	23069298	$98*((7^6+54-3)*2+1)$
22765968	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4/2-1)$	23070278	$98*((7^6+54+3)*2-1)$
22765986	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4/2+1)$	23070474	$98*((7^6+54+3)*2+1)$
22766076	$9*((8+(7^6+5)^4/2)-1)$	23070670	$98*((7^6-5+4^3)*2-1)$
22766094	$9*((8+(7^6+5)^4/2)+1)$	23072630	$98*((7^6+5+4^3)*2-1)$
22800777	$-9-87*(65-4^3*2+1)$	23072826	$98*((7^6+5+4^3)*2+1)$
22800795	$9-87*(65-4^3*2+1)$	23090858	$98*((7^6+54*3)*2-1)$
22800863	$-9-87*(65-4^3*2)-1$	23091054	$98*((7^6+54*3)*2+1)$
22800865	$-9-87*(65-4^3*2)+1$	23101246	$98*((7^6+5*43)*2-1)$
22800881	$9-87*(65-4^3*2)-1$	23101442	$98*((7^6+5*43)*2+1)$
22800883	$9-87*(65-4^3*2)+1$	23121198	$9+(87+6/5)*(4^3*2+1)$
22800951	$-9-87*(65-4^3*2-1)$	23121826	$98*((7^6+5*4^3)*2-1)$
22800969	$9-87*(65-4^3*2-1)$	23122022	$98*((7^6+5*4^3)*2+1)$
22803840	$9-87*(6*5-4^3*2+1)$	23176755	$-98+7^6*(5+4^3*(2+1))$
22804014	$9-87*(6*5-4^3*2-1)$	23176781	$-9*8+7^6*(5+4^3*(2+1))$
22805493	$9-87*(6+5-4^3*2+1)$	23176925	$9*8+7^6*(5+4^3*(2+1))$
22805667	$9-87*(6+5-4^3*2-1)$	23176951	$98+7^6*(5+4^3*(2+1))$
22806363	$9-87*(6-5-4^3*2+1)$	23181018	$98*((7^6+5^4-3)*2-1)$
22806711	$9+87*(6-5+4^3*2+1)$	23181214	$98*((7^6+5^4-3)*2+1)$
22807407	$9+87*(6+5+4^3*2-1)$	23182194	$98*((7^6+5^4+3)*2-1)$
22807581	$9+87*(6+5+4^3*2+1)$	23182390	$98*((7^6+5^4+3)*2+1)$
22809042	$-9+87*(6*5+4^3*2-1)$	23293440	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4*(43-21))$
22809060	$9+87*(6*5+4^3*2-1)$	23293584	$9*(8+(7^6-5)^4*(43-21))$
22809216	$-9+87*(6*5+4^3*2+1)$	23294421	$9*(-8+7^6*(54-32)-1)$
22809234	$9+87*(6*5+4^3*2+1)$	23294439	$9*(-8+7^6*(54-32)+1)$
22812087	$-9+87*(65+4^3*2-1)$	23294565	$9*(8+7^6*(54-32)-1)$
22812105	$9+87*(65+4^3*2-1)$	23294583	$9*(8+7^6*(54-32)+1)$
22812173	$-9+87*(65+4^3*2)-1$	23295420	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4*(43-21))$
22812175	$-9+87*(65+4^3*2)+1$	23295564	$9*(8+(7^6+5)^4*(43-21))$
22812191	$9+87*(65+4^3*2)-1$	23330736	$9+(8+7^6+5)^4*(4^3*2-1)$
22812193	$9+87*(65+4^3*2)+1$	23426606	$98*((7^6+5^4*3)*2-1)$
22812261	$-9+87*(65+4^3*2+1)$	23426802	$98*((7^6+5^4*3)*2+1)$
22812279	$9+87*(65+4^3*2+1)$	23442104	$(9/8/7*(6^5/4-3)^{\wedge}-2)^{\wedge}-1$
22861626	$9^8-7*((6+5)^4*3^2+1)$	23482944	$-9+87*(6^5+4^3*2-1)$
22861640	$9^8-7*((6+5)^4*3^2-1)$	23482962	$9+87*(6^5+4^3*2-1)$
22915728	$9*8*(7^6+5^4*321)$	23483118	$-9+87*(6^5+4^3*2+1)$
22936018	$98*((7^6-5^4*3)*2-1)$	23483136	$9+87*(6^5+4^3*2+1)$
22936214	$98*((7^6-5^4*3)*2+1)$	23529390	$(9+(8-7^6*5)^4*(3^2-1))$
22937194	$98*((7^6-5^4+3)*2-1)$	23529570	$(9-(8-7^6*5)^4*(3^2+1))$
22937390	$98*((7^6-5^4+3)*2+1)$	23529675	$9*(8*7^6-5)^4*(4/3)^2+1)$
22941867	$9*(8+7^6*5)^4*(4/3+2+1)$	23529702	$-98+7^6*5^4*(43-2-1)$
22996582	$98*((7^6-5^4*3)*2+1)$	23529898	$98+7^6*5^4*(43-2-1)$
23016966	$98*((7^6-5^4*3)*2-1)$	23530030	$(-9+(8+7^6*5)^4*(3^2+1))$
23017162	$98*((7^6-5^4*3)*2+1)$	23530210	$(9+(8+7^6*5)^4*(3^2+1))$
23027354	$98*((7^6-54*3)*2-1)$	23587256	$(9/8/7*(6^5/4+3)^{\wedge}-2)^{\wedge}-1$
23027550	$98*((7^6-54*3)*2+1)$	23646372	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4*(4/3+21))$
23045582	$98*((7^6-5-4^3)*2-1)$	23646516	$9*(8+(7^6-5)^4*(4/3+21))$
23045778	$98*((7^6-5-4^3)*2+1)$	23648382	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4*(4/3+21))$
23047738	$98*((7^6+5-4^3)*2+1)$	23648526	$9*(8+(7^6+5)^4*(4/3+21))$
23047934	$98*((7^6-54-3)*2-1)$	23747589	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)^3)*21)$
23048130	$98*((7^6-54-3)*2+1)$	23747733	$9*(8+(7^6+(5^4)^3)*21)$
23049110	$98*((7^6-54+3)*2-1)$	23822982	$9*(8+(7^6-5)^4*(43/2+1))$
23049306	$98*((7^6-54+3)*2+1)$	23824863	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4*(43/2+1))$
23049698	$98*((7^6-5-43)*2-1)$	23825007	$9*(8+(7^6+5)^4*(43/2+1))$
23049894	$98*((7^6-5-43)*2+1)$	23849098	$(-98+7)^4*(65-4^3*2+1)$
23051658	$98*((7^6+5-43)*2-1)$	23849280	$(-98+7)^4*(65-4^3*2-1)$
23051854	$98*((7^6+5-43)*2+1)$	23860928	$(98-7)^4*(65+4^3*2-1)$
23055578	$98*((7^6-54/3)*2-1)$	23861110	$(98-7)^4*(65+4^3*2+1)$
23057146	$-98*(7^6*(5-4-3)+21)$	23892544	$(9/(8*(7^6-5^4*3))^2)^{\wedge}-1$
23058567	$98*((7^6-5/4*3)*2+1)$	23999325	$(9+8)^4*((7^6-5)^4*3-2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
23999359	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^*3-2+1)$	24767062	$-9*8+7*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
23999393	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^*3+2-1)$	24767192	$9*8+7*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
23999427	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^*3+2+1)$	24767206	$9*8+7*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
24000298	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(43-2)-1)$	24767218	$98+7*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
24000494	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(43-2)-1)$	24811126	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$
24001365	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^*3-2-1)$	24882957	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*((5*4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
24001399	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^*3-2+1)$	24883443	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*((5*4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
24001433	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^*3+2-1)$	24904060	$(-9+8*(7+6))*((5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
24001467	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^*3+2+1)$	24904250	$(-9+8*(7+6))*((5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
24039409	$(9/(8/(7^{\wedge}6+5*4+3))^{\wedge}-1)$	24927280	$-98*(7+6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
24235596	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(43-2)+1)$	24927476	$-98*(7+6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
24235792	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(43-2)+1)$	24928652	$98*(7-6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
24282188	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	24928848	$98*(7-6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
24282256	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	24941490	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*43-2-1)$
24282290	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	24941686	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*43-2-1)$
24282358	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	25008816	$9*8*7^{\wedge}6*(5-43/21)$
24353082	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)-21)$	25159488	$(-9-87)*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
24353245	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)*(2+1)$	25159680	$(-9-87)*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
24353252	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)-2)-1$	25171968	$(9+87)*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
24353254	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)-2)+1$	25172160	$(9+87)*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
24353288	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)+2)-1$	25176788	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*43-2+1)$
24353290	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)+2)+1$	25176984	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*43-2+1)$
24353396	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)-2)-1$	25277112	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3+21))$
24353398	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)-2)+1$	25277256	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3+21))$
24353432	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)+2)-1$	25294896	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6-543)*(2+1)$
24353434	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)+2)+1$	25395120	$9*((8/7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*3-21)$
24353441	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)*(2+1)$	25395498	$9*((8/7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*3+21)$
24353460	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)+21)$	25397523	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-543)*(2+1)$
24373799	$9*(8*(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	25399008	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3-21$
24373801	$9*(8*(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	25399371	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
24378843	$9-(87+6)*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	25400331	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3-21)$
24379029	$9-(87+6)*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	25400367	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*3-2)-1)$
24379773	$9+(87+6)*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	25400385	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*3-2)+1)$
24379959	$9+(87+6)*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	25400493	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3-2-1)$
24452022	$-98+7*((6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	25400547	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3+2+1)$
24452036	$-98+7*((6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	25400655	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*3+2)-1)$
24452048	$9*-8+7*((6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	25400673	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*3+2)+1)$
24452062	$9*-8+7*((6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	25400709	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3+21)$
24452192	$9*8+7*((6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	25402032	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3+21$
24452206	$9*8+7*((6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	25407719	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3-2-1$
24452218	$98+7*((6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	25407721	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3-2+1$
24452232	$98+7*((6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	25407783	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3)^*(2+1)$
24484065	$(9/(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2)))^{\wedge}-1$	25407845	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3-2)-1$
24504312	$98*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	25407847	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3-2)+1$
24504508	$98*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	25407881	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3+2)-1$
24504704	$98*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+2-1)$	25407883	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3+2)+1$
24504900	$98*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+2+1)$	25407945	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)+3)^*(2+1)$
24538021	$(9/((8+7^{\wedge}6)*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$	25408007	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3+2-1$
24608924	$-9*(8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)))^{\wedge}-1$	25408009	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3+2+1$
24608926	$-9*(8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)))^{\wedge}+1$	25409832	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*54*(5+4))^*(3+21)$
24609068	$9*(8-7*(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)))^{\wedge}-1$	25410051	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3-21)$
24609070	$9*(8-7*(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)))^{\wedge}+1$	25410429	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3+21)$
24609680	$9*(-8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)))^{\wedge}-1$	25410537	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-54)*3-21$
24609682	$9*(-8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)))^{\wedge}+1$	25410780	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)-4*3)^*(2+1)$
24609824	$9*(8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)))^{\wedge}-1$	25410959	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*4*3)^*2-1$
24609826	$9*(8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)))^{\wedge}+1$	25410961	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*4*3)^*2+1$
24627106	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3)^*2-1)$	25411031	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*4*3^*2)-1$
24627302	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$	25411033	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*4*3^*2)+1$
24662799	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4/3^*2+1)$	25411175	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*4*3^*2)-1$
24702174	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43-2+1)$	25411177	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*4*3^*2)+1$
24705777	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5/4-3)^*21$	25411428	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)+4*3)^*(2+1)$
24705795	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5/4-3)^*21$	25411792	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3+2-1)$
24705963	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43-2+1)$	25412161	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3+2-1)$
24706192	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(43-2+1)$	25412207	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3+2-1)$
24706388	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(43-2+1)$	25412225	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3+2-1)$
24706626	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+(3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$	25412385	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3+21)$
24706635	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43-2+1)$	25412576	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3+2-1)$
24706803	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5/4+3)^*21$	25412940	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)-4*3)^*(2+1)$
24710406	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43-2+1)$	25413119	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4*3)^*2-1$
24767022	$-98+7*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	25413121	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4*3)^*2+1$
24767036	$-98+7*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	25413191	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4*3^*2)-1$
24767048	$-9*8+7*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	25413193	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4*3^*2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
25413335	$9^*(8+(7^6+5)^4*3^2)-1$	25734800	$98^*(7^6+5+4^3*2+1)$
25413337	$9^*(8+(7^6+5)^4*3^2)+1$	25828065	$((9^8-7+6)/5+4)^3+21$
25413588	$9^*(8^*(7^6+5)+4^3)^*(2+1)$	25878468	$(-98+7^6*5)^*(43+2-1)$
25413831	$9^*((8^*7^6+54)^3+21)$	25882437	$9-(8-7^6*5)^*(43+2-1)$
25413939	$9^*(8^*(7^6+5+4)^3-21)$	25882682	$-98+7^6*5^*(43+2-1)$
25414317	$9^*(8^*(7^6+5+4)^3+21)$	25882878	$98+7^6*5^*(43+2-1)$
25414536	$(98+7^6*(5+4))^*(3+21)$	25883123	$-9+(8+7^6*5)^*(43+2-1)$
25416359	$9^*8^*((7^6+5^4)^3-2)-1$	25883141	$9+(8+7^6*5)^*(43+2-1)$
25416361	$9^*8^*((7^6+5^4)^3-2)+1$	25887092	$(98+7^6*5)^*(43+2-1)$
25416423	$9^*(8^*(7^6+5^4)-3)^*(2+1)$	25898589	$((9^8+7^6)/5-4)^3+21$
25416485	$9^*(8^*(7^6+5^4)^3-2)-1$	25898655	$((9^8+7^6)/5+4)^3+21$
25416487	$9^*(8^*(7^6+5^4)^3-2)+1$	25940404	$98^*((7^6-5)/4^3*2-1)$
25416521	$9^*(8^*(7^6+5^4)^3+2)-1$	25940600	$98^*((7^6-5)/4^3*2+1)$
25416523	$9^*(8^*(7^6+5^4)^3+2)+1$	25942609	$98^*((7^6+5)/4^3*2-1)$
25416585	$9^*(8^*(7^6+5^4)+3)^*(2+1)$	25942805	$98^*((7^6+5)/4^3*2+1)$
25416647	$9^*8^*((7^6+5^4)^3+2)-1$	25951374	$9^*(-87+(6+5)^*(4^3*2-1))$
25416649	$9^*8^*((7^6+5^4)^3+2)+1$	25951464	$9^*(-87+(6+5)^4*3^2-1)$
25422336	$9^*8^*((7^6+54)^3-21)$	25951482	$9^*(-87+(6+5)^4*3^2+1)$
25423659	$9^*(8^*(7^6+54)^3-21)$	25951572	$9^*(-87+(6+5)^*(4^3*2+1))$
25423695	$9^*(8^*((7^6+54)^3-2)-1)$	25951751	$9^*(-8^*7+(6+5)^4*3^2-1)$
25423713	$9^*(8^*((7^6+54)^3-2)+1)$	25952120	$9^*(-8-7+(6+5)^4*3^2-1)$
25423821	$9^*(8^*(7^6+54)^3-2-1)$	25952122	$9^*(-8-7+(6+5)^4*3^2+1)$
25423875	$9^*(8^*(7^6+54)^3+2+1)$	25952759	$9^*(8^*7+(6+5)^4*3^2-1)$
25423983	$9^*(8^*((7^6+54)^3+2)-1)$	25952761	$9^*(8^*7+(6+5)^4*3^2+1)$
25424001	$9^*(8^*((7^6+54)^3+2)+1)$	25953138	$9^*(87+(6+5)^*(4^3*2+1))$
25424037	$9^*(8^*(7^6+54)^3+21)$	25986891	$9^8-(7^6+5)^*(4^3)^2+1$
25425360	$9^*8^*((7^6+54)^3+21)$	25988341	$9^8-(7^6-5)^*(4^3)^2+1$
25426845	$9^*(8^*7^6+543)^*(2+1)$	25999307	$(9+8)^*((7^6-5)^*(4+3^2)-1)$
25428870	$9^*((8^*7^6+5^4)^3-21)$	25999341	$(9+8)^*((7^6-5)^*(4+3^2)+1)$
25429248	$9^*((8^*7^6+5^4)^3+21)$	26000412	$(9+8)^*7^6*(5+4^3/2)-1$
25515836	$(9/(876*(5+4^3*2)))^{\wedge-1}$	26000446	$(9+8)^*(7^6*5+4^3/2)+1$
25529472	$9^*8^*(7^6+543)^*(2+1)$	26001517	$(9+8)^*((7^6+5)^*(4+3^2)-1)$
25546995	$9^*(8^*(7^6+5^4)^3-21)$	26001551	$(9+8)^*((7^6+5)^*(4+3^2)+1)$
25547373	$9^*(8^*(7^6+5^4)^3+21)$	26007296	$9^8-(7+6)^5*(4^3*2+1)$
25634669	$9^8-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2-1)$	26007348	$9^8-(7+6)^*(5^4*3^2+1)$
25645424	$-98^*(7^6-5-4^3*2+1)$	26007374	$9^8-(7+6)^*(5^4*3^2-1)$
25645521	$-98^*(7^6-5-4^3*2)-1$	26007426	$9^8-(7+6)^5*(4^3*2-1)$
25645523	$-98^*(7^6-5-4^3*2)+1$	26214265	$(-9+8^7/(6/5))^*(4^3+2+1)$
25645620	$-98^*(7^6-5-4^3*2-1)$	26214535	$(9+8^7/(6/5))^*(4^3+2+1)$
25647384	$-98+7^6*(5^4+3+2+1)$	26222199	$9^8-(7^6+5)^*(4^3)^2-1$
25647580	$98+7^6*(5^4+3+2+1)$	26223629	$9^8-(7^6-5)^*(4^3)^2-1$
25661979	$(98-7/65)^*(4^3*2+1)$	26265816	$(9+8)^*((7-6^5*5^4/3)^2-1)$
25669434	$-98^*(7^6*5-4^3*2+1)$	26265850	$(9+8)^*((7-6^5*5^4/3)^2+1)$
25669630	$-98^*(7^6*5-4^3*2-1)$	26313937	$(-9+8^7)^*(6^{\wedge-5+4^3})^2-1$
25682958	$-98^*(7+65-4^3*2+1)$	26314031	$(-9+8^7)^*(6^{\wedge-5+4^3})^2+1$
25684330	$98^*(7-65+4^3*2-1)$	26352257	$9-8^*((7^6-5)^*(4-32)+1)$
25684526	$98^*(7-65+4^3*2+1)$	26352273	$9-8^*((7^6-5)^*(4-32)-1)$
25688250	$-98^*(7+6+5-4^3*2+1)$	26354497	$9-8^*((7^6+5)^*(4-32)+1)$
25688446	$-98^*(7+6+5-4^3*2-1)$	26354513	$9-8^*((7^6+5)^*(4-32)-1)$
25689230	$-98^*(7+6-5-4^3*2+1)$	26451376	$-98^*(7-6^5-4^3*2+1)$
25689916	$-98^*((7-6)^5-4^3*2+1)$	26451572	$-98^*(7-6^5-4^3*2-1)$
25690000	$-98^*(7^{\wedge-6+5})-4^3*2+1$	26452748	$98^*(7+6^5+4^3*2-1)$
25690023	$9+(87+6+5)^*(4^3*2-1)$	26453854	$-98+7^*(6^5/4)^{\wedge(3-2+1)}$
25690196	$-98^*(7^{\wedge-6+5})-4^3*2-1$	26453879	$-9^*(8-7^*(6^5/4/3)^2)-1$
25690219	$9+(87+6+5)^*(4^3*2+1)$	26453881	$-9^*(8-7^*(6^5/4/3)^2)+1$
25690406	$-98^*(7-6-5-4^3*2+1)$	26454023	$9^*(8+7^*(6^5/4/3)^2)-1$
25692268	$-98^*(7-6^5-4^3*2+1)$	26454025	$9^*(8+7^*(6^5/4/3)^2)+1$
25692464	$-98^*(7-6^5-4^3*2-1)$	26454050	$98+7^*(6^5/4)^{\wedge(3-2+1)}$
25694620	$98^*(7^6+5+4^3*2-1)$	26470772	$9^*(-8+(7^6*5-4)^*(3+2))-1$
25694816	$98^*(7^6+5+4^3*2+1)$	26470774	$9^*(-8+(7^6*5-4)^*(3+2))+1$
25695698	$-98^*(7-65-4^3*2+1)$	26470916	$9^*(8+(7^6*5-4)^*(3+2))-1$
25695894	$-98^*(7-65-4^3*2-1)$	26470918	$9^*(8+(7^6*5-4)^*(3+2))+1$
25696384	$98^*((7+6)^5+4^3*2-1)$	26471132	$9^*(-8+(7^6*5+4)^*(3+2))-1$
25696580	$98^*((7+6)^5+4^3*2+1)$	26471134	$9^*(-8+(7^6*5+4)^*(3+2))+1$
25697266	$98^*(7+65+4^3*2+1)$	26471276	$9^*(8+(7^6*5+4)^*(3+2))-1$
25697560	$98^*(7^*(6+5)+4^3*2-1)$	26471278	$9^*(8+(7^6*5+4)^*(3+2))+1$
25697756	$98^*(7^*(6+5)+4^3*2+1)$	26561888	$9^*(-8+76)^*((5^4/3)^2-1)$
25710790	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3*2+1)$	26562423	$-9-(8-76)^*(5^4^{\wedge(3/2)}-1)$
25718441	$(98+7/65)^*(4^3*2+1)$	26562441	$-9-(8-76)^*(5^4^{\wedge(3/2)}-1)$
25734604	$98^*(7^6+5+4^3*2-1)$	26562559	$-9-(8-76)^*(5^4^{\wedge(3/2)}+1)$
25734701	$98^*(7^6+5+4^3*2)-1$	26562577	$-9-(8-76)^*(5^4^{\wedge(3/2)}+1)$
25734703	$98^*(7^6+5+4^3*2)+1$	26563112	$9^*(-8+76)^*((5^4/3)^2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
26583228	$9/8^{\wedge}-7/6^{\wedge} * ((5/4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	28588906	$9^{\wedge} * ((8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5+4))^{\wedge}3-2)+1$
26588576	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge} * (43+2)+1)$	28588940	$9^{\wedge} * ((8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5+4))^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
26588772	$98+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge} * (43+2)+1)$	28588942	$9^{\wedge} * ((8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5+4))^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
26738705	$(9+8)^{\wedge} * ((7-6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	28589112	$9^{\wedge} * ((8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5+4))^{\wedge}3+21)$
26751550	$-98^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	28589850	$-9^{\wedge} * (8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge} * (4-32+1))$
26751746	$-98^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	28589994	$9^{\wedge} * (8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge} * (4-32+1))$
26775825	$-9^{\wedge} * (8+(7-65^{\wedge}4/3)/2+1)$	28601757	$9^{\wedge} * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
26775888	$9^{\wedge} * (-8+(7+65^{\wedge}4/3)/2-1)$	28601829	$9^{\wedge}-8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}21$
26775987	$9^{\wedge} * (8-(7-65^{\wedge}4/3)/2+1)$	28601901	$9^{\wedge} * (8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
26776050	$9^{\wedge} * (8+(7+65^{\wedge}4/3)/2+1)$	28706258	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge} * (4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
26823955	$-9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (54+3)/2-1)$	28706284	$-9^{\wedge} * 8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge} * (4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
26823989	$9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (54+3)/2+1)$	28706428	$9^{\wedge} * 8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge} * (4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
26843542	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^{\wedge}4)/(3/2+1)$	28706454	$98+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge} * (4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
26860816	$(9+8)^{\wedge} * ((7+6^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	28810775	$98^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge} * (3/2+1)$
26860850	$(9+8)^{\wedge} * ((7+6^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	28820771	$98^{\wedge} * ((7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
26982663	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge}4/3+21)$	28820967	$98^{\wedge} * ((7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$
26982681	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge}4/3+21)$	28821996	$98^{\wedge} * ((7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5-43)/2+1)$
27003312	$9^{\wedge} * (8+(7+65^{\wedge}4/3)/2+1)$	28822682	$98^{\wedge} * ((7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge} * (4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
27054762	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * 5)^{\wedge} * (43+2+1)$	28822878	$98^{\wedge} * ((7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge} * (4-3/2)+1)$
27058911	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * 5)^{\wedge} * (43+2+1)$	28823870	$(98^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge} * (3/2+1)$
27059172	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * 5^{\wedge} * (43+2+1)$	28824140	$(98^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge} * (3/2+1)$
27059368	$98+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * 5^{\wedge} * (43+2+1)$	28825328	$98^{\wedge} * ((7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge} * (4-3/2)+1)$
27059629	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * 5)^{\wedge} * (43+2+1)$	28826014	$98^{\wedge} * ((7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5+43)/2-1)$
27059647	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * 5)^{\wedge} * (43+2+1)$	28827043	$98^{\wedge} * ((7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
27063778	$(98+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * 5)^{\wedge} * (43+2+1)$	28827239	$98^{\wedge} * ((7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$
27083565	$9^{\wedge} * (8+7)^{\wedge} * (-6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}321)$	28837235	$98^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge} * (3/2+1)$
27085185	$9^{\wedge} * (8+7)^{\wedge} * (6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}321)$	28941556	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge} * (4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
27163998	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * 5+4)^{\wedge} * 3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	28941582	$-9^{\wedge} * 8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge} * (4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
27164214	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * 5-4)^{\wedge} * 3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	28941726	$9^{\wedge} * 8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge} * (4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
27293263	$(-9+8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6/5)^{\wedge} * ((4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	28941752	$98+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge} * (4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
27293417	$9-8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge} * (4-32-1)$	29021943	$-9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
27295737	$9-8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge} * (4-32-1)$	29021961	$9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
27295873	$(9+8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6/5)^{\wedge} * ((4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	29059205	$-98-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}21)$
27367947	$9+8^{\wedge} * 6/5^{\wedge} * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	29059401	$98-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}21)$
27518190	$(-98-7)^{\wedge} * (65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	29092391	$9^{\wedge} * (8^{\wedge} * (7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
27518400	$(-98-7)^{\wedge} * (65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	29092393	$9^{\wedge} * (8^{\wedge} * (7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
27531840	$(98+7)^{\wedge} * (65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	29157568	$-9+(8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
27532050	$(98+7)^{\wedge} * (65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	29157586	$9+(8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
27662944	$(9+8)/(7/((6+5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2)-1))$	29163551	$-9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
27692352	$9^{\wedge} * (8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(5+4-3)^{\wedge}21)$	29163569	$9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
27822597	$(9+8)^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * 5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1))$	29172001	$9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
27999255	$(9+8)^{\wedge} * ((7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge} * (4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$	29174711	$-9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
27999289	$(9+8)^{\wedge} * ((7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge} * (4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	29174729	$9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28000471	$9-8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5/4-32+1)$	29175269	$-9+(8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28001635	$(9+8)^{\wedge} * ((7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge} * (4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$	29175287	$9+(8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28001669	$(9+8)^{\wedge} * ((7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge} * (4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	29175597	$9+(8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-5)-4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28079920	$98^{\wedge} * ((7/(6^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}4-3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	29175827	$-9+(8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-5)+4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28080116	$98^{\wedge} * ((7/(6^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}4-3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	29175845	$9+(8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-5)+4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28119519	$9^{\wedge} * (8^{\wedge} * (-76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1)$	29176341	$9+(8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28119537	$9^{\wedge} * (8^{\wedge} * (-76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))+1)$	29176651	$9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-5/4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28130463	$9^{\wedge} * (8^{\wedge} * (76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1)$	29176713	$9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28130481	$9^{\wedge} * (8^{\wedge} * (76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))+1)$	29176992	$9+(8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28217343	$9^{\wedge} * (8^{\wedge} * (7+6+5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2-1$	29177209	$9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28217345	$9^{\wedge} * (8^{\wedge} * (7+6+5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2+1$	29177240	$9+(8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28235662	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * 5^{\wedge} * ((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	29177253	$-9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+5/4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28235858	$98+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * 5^{\wedge} * ((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	29177271	$9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+5/4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28236144	$(9/((8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * 5)^{\wedge}432))^{\wedge}2-1$	29178077	$9+(8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+5)-4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28553455	$(9+8)^{\wedge} * ((7-6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	29178325	$9+(8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+5)+4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28553489	$(9+8)^{\wedge} * ((7-6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	29178617	$-9+(8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28575513	$9^{\wedge} * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge} * 3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	29178635	$9+(8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28575657	$9^{\wedge} * (8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge} * 3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	29179193	$9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28579707	$9^{\wedge} * ((87+6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	29181921	$9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28579725	$9^{\wedge} * ((87+6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	29190335	$-9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28587420	$-9^{\wedge} * (8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge} * (4-32+1))$	29190353	$9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28587564	$9^{\wedge} * (8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge} * (4-32+1))$	29196318	$-9+(8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28588446	$9^{\wedge} * (-8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5+4)^{\wedge} * 3-21)$	29196336	$9+(8^{\wedge} * 7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28588472	$9^{\wedge} * ((-8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5+4))^{\wedge} * 3-2)-1$	29281788	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (54+3^{\wedge}21)$
28588474	$9^{\wedge} * ((-8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5+4))^{\wedge} * 3-2)+1$	29294529	$9^{\wedge} * (-8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge} * (4/3+21)))$
28588508	$9^{\wedge} * ((-8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5+4))^{\wedge} * 3+2)-1$	29294673	$9^{\wedge} * (8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5^{\wedge} * (4/3+21)))$
28588510	$9^{\wedge} * ((-8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5+4))^{\wedge} * 3+2)+1$	29331943	$-9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28588824	$9^{\wedge} * (-8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5+4)^{\wedge} * 3+21)$	29331961	$9+8^{\wedge} * (7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge} * (32-1)$
28588904	$9^{\wedge} * ((8+7^{\wedge}6^{\wedge} * (5+4))^{\wedge} * 3-2)-1$	29374839	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge} * ((6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
29374853	$9^8 - 7 * ((6 - 5 + 4)^3 - 2)$	30239072	$9 * (8 + (7 * 6 - 5^4 * 3)^2) - 1$
29513737	$(9^8 - 7^6) * (54 / 32 - 1)$	30239074	$9 * (8 + (7 * 6 - 5^4 * 3)^2) + 1$
29529801	$-98 - 7^6 * (5 - 4^3 + 2 - 1)$	30269775	$(9 + 8) * (7 * (-6^5 + 4^3 * 3^2) - 1)$
29529997	$98 - 7^6 * (5 - 4^3 + 2 - 1)$	30269809	$(-9 - 8) * (7 * (6^5 - 4^3 * 3^2) - 1)$
29644230	$(-98 + (7^6 - 5) * 4^3) * 21$	30278127	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4) * 32 - 1)$
29645490	$(-98 + 7^6 * (5 + 4 + 3)) * 21$	30278143	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4) * 32 + 1)$
29645793	$9 - (8 - (7^6 - 5) * 4) * 3 * 21$	30278145	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4) * 32 - 1)$
29646129	$9 - (8 - (7^6 - 5) * 4^3) * 21$	30278161	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4) * 32 + 1)$
29646190	$-98 + (7^6 - 5) * 4^3 * 21$	30340089	$9^8 - (7^6 + 5) * 4^3 * 3^2 + 1$
29646207	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 - 5) * (4 - 32) + 1)$	30341169	$9^8 - (7^6 - 5) * 4^3 * 3^2 + 1$
29646386	$98 + (7^6 - 5) * 4^3 * 21$	30451191	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4 * 3)^2 - 1)$
29646465	$9 + (8 + (7^6 - 5) * 4^3) * 21$	30451207	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4 * 3)^2 + 1)$
29646750	$(-98 + (7^6 + 5) * 4^3) * 21$	30451209	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4 * 3)^2 - 1)$
29647389	$9 - (8 - 7^6 * (5 + 4 + 3)) * 21$	30451225	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4 * 3)^2 + 1)$
29647707	$-9 + (8 + 7^6 * (5 + 4 + 3)) * 21$	30635150	$-98 + (7 / ((6 + 5)^4 + 3)^2)^{-1}$
29647725	$9 + (8 + 7^6 * (5 + 4 + 3)) * 21$	30635176	$-9 * 8 + (7 / ((6 + 5)^4 + 3)^2)^{-1}$
29648346	$(98 + (7^6 - 5) * 4^3) * 21$	30635320	$9 * 8 + (7 / ((6 + 5)^4 + 3)^2)^{-1}$
29648649	$9 - (8 - (7^6 + 5) * 4^3) * 21$	30635346	$98 + (7 / ((6 + 5)^4 + 3)^2)^{-1}$
29648710	$-98 + (7^6 + 5) * 4^3 * 21$	30670190	$-9 * (8 + (7 + 6) * (5 - 4^3 * 3^2)) - 1$
29648727	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4 - 32) + 1)$	30670192	$-9 * (8 + (7 + 6) * (5 - 4^3 * 3^2)) + 1$
29648906	$98 + (7^6 + 5) * 4^3 * 21$	30670740	$9 + (87 + 6 * 5) * (4^3 * 3^2 - 1)$
29648985	$9 + (8 + (7^6 + 5) * 4^3) * 21$	30670956	$-9 + (87 + 6 * 5) * (4^3 * 3^2 + 1)$
29649321	$9 + (8 + (7^6 + 5) * 4) * 3 * 21$	30670974	$9 + (87 + 6 * 5) * (4^3 * 3^2 + 1)$
29649606	$(98 + 7^6 * (5 + 4 + 3)) * 21$	30671360	$9 * (-8 + (7 + 6) * (5 + 4^3 * 3^2)) - 1$
29650866	$(98 + (7^6 + 5) * 4^3) * 21$	30671362	$9 * (-8 + (7 + 6) * (5 + 4^3 * 3^2)) + 1$
29882855	$9 - 8 * 7^6 * (5 / 4 - 32 - 1)$	30671504	$9 * (8 + (7 + 6) * (5 + 4^3 * 3^2)) - 1$
29958127	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5^4) * 32 - 1)$	30671506	$9 * (8 + (7 + 6) * (5 + 4^3 * 3^2)) + 1$
29958143	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5^4) * 32 + 1)$	30705012	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 - 5) * (4 - 32 - 1))$
29958145	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5^4) * 32 - 1)$	30705156	$9 * (8 - (7^6 - 5) * (4 - 32 - 1))$
29958161	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5^4) * 32 + 1)$	30706291	$-98 + 7^6 * (5 + 4^3 * 3^2 - 1)$
29999883	$(9 + 8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4^3) * (2 + 1)$	30706487	$98 + 7^6 * (5 + 4^3 * 3^2 - 1)$
30000240	$(9 + 8) * ((7^6 * 5 - 4) * 3 - 2 - 1)$	30707622	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4 - 32 - 1))$
30000274	$(9 + 8) * ((7^6 * 5 - 4) * 3 - 2 + 1)$	30707766	$9 * (8 - (7^6 + 5) * (4 - 32 - 1))$
30000308	$(9 + 8) * ((7^6 * 5 - 4) * 3 + 2 - 1)$	30719981	$9 * ((8^8 / (7 - 6) / 5)^{-4/3 - 2}) - 1$
30000427	$(9 + 8) * (7^6 * 5 - 4 / 3) * (2 + 1)$	30719983	$9 * ((8^8 / (7 - 6) / 5)^{-4/3 - 2}) + 1$
30000478	$(9 + 8) * (7^6 * (5^4 - 3 - 2) - 1)$	30720017	$9 * ((8^8 / (7 - 6) / 5)^{-4/3 + 2}) - 1$
30000512	$(9 + 8) * (7^6 * (5^4 - 3 - 2) + 1)$	30720019	$9 * ((8^8 / (7 - 6) / 5)^{-4/3 + 2}) + 1$
30000563	$(9 + 8) * ((7^6 * 5 + 4 / 3) * (2 + 1))$	30725906	$9^8 - (7^6 * 5) * (4^3 * 3^2 + 1)$
30000682	$(9 + 8) * ((7^6 * 5 + 4) * 3 - 2 + 1)$	30726000	$9^8 - (7^6 * 5) * (4^3 * 3^2 - 1)$
30000716	$(9 + 8) * ((7^6 * 5 + 4) * 3 + 2 - 1)$	30827566	$-98 * (7 - 6 / 5 * (4^3 * 3^2 + 1))$
30000750	$(9 + 8) * ((7^6 * 5 + 4) * 3 + 2 + 1)$	30876608	$9 / ((8 * (7 - 6^4 * (-5 + 4)))^{-3/21})$
30001107	$(9 + 8) * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3) * (2 + 1)$	30894327	$-9 + 8 * (7^6 - 5^4) * (32 + 1)$
30015751	$9 * 8 / ((7 - 6^5 / 4) / 3)^{-2 - 1}$	30894345	$9 + 8 * (7^6 - 5^4) * (32 + 1)$
30015753	$9 * 8 / ((7 - 6^5 / 4) / 3)^{-2 + 1}$	31024350	$98 * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 * 3^2 - 1)$
30104303	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5^4) * 32 - 1)$	31024546	$98 * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 * 3^2 + 1)$
30104319	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5^4) * 32 + 1)$	31038702	$-9 + (8 * 7^6 - 5^4) * (32 + 1)$
30104321	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5^4) * 32 - 1)$	31038720	$9 + (8 * 7^6 - 5^4) * (32 + 1)$
30104337	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5^4) * 32 + 1)$	31045071	$-9 + 8 * (7^6 - 5^4) * (32 + 1)$
30113025	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5^4) * 32 - 1)$	31045089	$9 + 8 * (7^6 - 5^4) * (32 + 1)$
30113041	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5^4) * 32 + 1)$	31054065	$9 + 8 * (7^6 - 5^4) * (32 + 1)$
30115823	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5 - 4) * 32 - 1)$	31056951	$-9 + 8 * (7^6 - 5 - 4) * (32 + 1)$
30115839	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5 - 4) * 32 + 1)$	31056969	$9 + 8 * (7^6 - 5 - 4) * (32 + 1)$
30115841	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5 - 4) * 32 - 1)$	31057545	$-9 + (8 * 7^6 - 5^4) * (32 + 1)$
30115857	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5 - 4) * 32 + 1)$	31057563	$9 + (8 * 7^6 - 5^4) * (32 + 1)$
30117841	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5 / 4) * 32 + 1)$	31057875	$-9 + (8 * (7^6 - 5) - 4) * (32 + 1)$
30117905	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 - 5 + 4) * 32 + 1)$	31057893	$9 + (8 * (7^6 - 5) - 4) * (32 + 1)$
30118417	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5 - 4) * 32 + 1)$	31058139	$-9 + (8 * (7^6 - 5) + 4) * (32 + 1)$
30118447	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5 / 4) * 32 - 1)$	31058157	$9 + (8 * (7^6 - 5) + 4) * (32 + 1)$
30118481	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5 / 4) * 32 + 1)$	31058685	$9 + (8 * 7^6 - 5^4) * (32 + 1)$
30120449	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5 + 4) * 32 - 1)$	31058997	$-9 + 8 * (7^6 - 5 / 4) * (32 + 1)$
30120465	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5 + 4) * 32 + 1)$	31059015	$9 + 8 * (7^6 - 5 / 4) * (32 + 1)$
30123263	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4) * 32 + 1)$	31059048	$9 + (8 * 7^6 - 5 - 4) * (32 + 1)$
30123265	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4) * 32 - 1)$	31059063	$-9 + 8 * (7^6 - 5 + 4) * (32 + 1)$
30123281	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4) * 32 + 1)$	31059081	$9 + 8 * (7^6 - 5 + 4) * (32 + 1)$
30131951	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4) * 32 - 1)$	31059312	$9 + (8 * 7^6 - 5 + 4) * (32 + 1)$
30131967	$-9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4) * 32 + 1)$	31059378	$9 + (8 * 7^6 + 5 - 4) * (32 + 1)$
30131969	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4) * 32 - 1)$	31059525	$9 * (8 * 7^6 * (5 - 4 / 3) + 21)$
30131985	$9 + 8 * ((7^6 + 5^4) * 32 + 1)$	31059609	$9 + 8 * (7^6 + 5 - 4) * (32 + 1)$
30235695	$-98 + 7^6 * (5 + 4^3 * 21)$	31059642	$9 + (8 * 7^6 + 5 + 4) * (32 + 1)$
30235891	$98 + 7^6 * (5 + 4^3 * 21)$	31059657	$-9 + 8 * (7^6 + 5 / 4) * (32 + 1)$
30238928	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 - 5^4 * 3)^2) - 1$	31059675	$9 + 8 * (7^6 + 5 / 4) * (32 + 1)$
30238930	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 - 5^4 * 3)^2) + 1$	31060005	$9 + (8 * 7^6 + 5^4) * (32 + 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
31060533	$9+(8*(7^6+5)-4)*(32+1)$	31842657	$9*(-87+(6+5^4*3)^2-1)$
31060779	$-9+(8*(7^6+5)+4)*(32+1)$	31842675	$9*(-87+(6+5^4*3)^2+1)$
31060797	$9+(8*(7^6+5)+4)*(32+1)$	31842944	$9*(-8*7+(6+5^4*3)^2)-1$
31061109	$-9+(8*7^6+54)*(32+1)$	31842946	$9*(-8*7+(6+5^4*3)^2)+1$
31061127	$9+(8*7^6+54)*(32+1)$	31843313	$9*(-8-7+(6+5^4*3)^2)-1$
31061721	$9+8*(7^6+5+4)*(32+1)$	31843315	$9*(-8-7+(6+5^4*3)^2)+1$
31064607	$-9+8*(7^6+5*4)*(32+1)$	31843583	$9*(8+7+(6+5^4*3)^2)-1$
31064625	$9+8*(7^6+5*4)*(32+1)$	31843585	$9*(8+7+(6+5^4*3)^2)+1$
31073583	$-9+8*(7^6+54)*(32+1)$	31843952	$9*(8*7+(6+5^4*3)^2)-1$
31073601	$9+8*(7^6+54)*(32+1)$	31843954	$9*(8*7+(6+5^4*3)^2)+1$
31079952	$-9+(8*7^6+5^4)*(32+1)$	31844223	$9*(87+(6+5^4*3)^2-1)$
31079970	$9+(8*7^6+5^4)*(32+1)$	31844241	$9*(87+(6+5^4*3)^2+1)$
31191549	$(-9-8)*(7*(6*5-4^3)^2)+1$	31876841	$9+8*76/5*(4^3)^2+1$
31191583	$(9+8)*(-7*(6*5-4^3)^2)+1$	31933800	$9/((87*65-4)/3)^2-2-1$
31193810	$(-9-8)*(7*(6+5-4^3)^2)+1$	31933802	$9/((87*65-4)/3)^2-2+1$
31193844	$(-9-8)*(7*(6+5-4^3)^2)-1$	31957800	$98*(7^6*5-4^3)^2-1$
31195000	$(-9-8)*(7*(6-5-4^3)^2)+1$	31957996	$98*(7^6*5-4^3)^2+1$
31195034	$(-9-8)*(7*(6-5-4^3)^2)-1$	32080823	$9*(-8+(7+6+5^4*3)^2)-1$
31195119	$(9+8)*(7*(6-5)^4)^3^2-1$	32080825	$9*(-8+(7+6+5^4*3)^2)+1$
31195153	$(9+8)*(7*(6-5)^4)^3^2+1$	32080967	$9*(8+(7+6+5^4*3)^2)-1$
31195238	$(9+8)*(7*(6-5+4^3)^2)-1$	32080969	$9*(8+(7+6+5^4*3)^2)+1$
31195272	$(9+8)*(7*(6-5+4^3)^2)+1$	32120463	$(9+8)*(7*(6^5+4^3)^2)-1$
31196428	$(9+8)*(7*(6+5+4^3)^2)-1$	32120497	$(9+8)*(7*(6^5+4^3)^2)+1$
31196462	$(9+8)*(7*(6+5+4^3)^2)+1$	32226645	$9*(8+7/6)*(5^4)^{(3/2)+1}$
31198689	$(9+8)*(7*(6^5+4^3)^2)-1$	32649624	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
31198723	$(9+8)*(7*(6^5+4^3)^2)+1$	32649768	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
31203323	$9*(-8+(7+6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	32808933	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
31203325	$9*(-8+(7+6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	32809077	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
31203467	$9*(8+(7+6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	32811744	$9*(8+76)*((5^4/3)^2)-1$
31203469	$9*(8+(7+6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	32812407	$-9+(8+76)*((5^4/3)^2)+1$
31224327	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4)*(32+1)$	32812425	$9+(8+76)*(5^4)^{(3/2)-1}$
31224345	$9+8*(7^6+5^4)*(32+1)$	32812575	$-9+(8+76)*(5^4)^{(3/2)+1}$
31294536	$98*(7^6*(5/(4+3)+2)-1)$	32812593	$9+(8+76)*(5^4)^{(3/2)+1}$
31294651	$9+8*(7^6*(5/4+32)+1)$	32813256	$9*((8+76)*((5^4/3)^2+1))$
31294732	$98*(7^6*(5/(4+3)+2)+1)$	32818419	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
31295970	$9^8(-8+7+6)*((5^4+3)^2+1)$	32818563	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
31361790	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4-3)/21)$	32821033	$(-98+7^6*(5+4))^3)^2-1$
31361934	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4-3)/21)$	32821488	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
31399470	$9^8-7^6*(5^4*(3+2)-1)$	32821632	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
31437657	$9*(-87+(6-5^4*3)^2-1)$	32823720	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
31437675	$9*(-87+(6-5^4*3)^2+1)$	32823832	$9-(8-7^6*(5+4))^3)^2-1$
31437944	$-9*(8*7-(6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	32823973	$-98+7^6*(5+4)^3)^2-1$
31437946	$-9*(8*7-(6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	32824169	$98+7^6*(5+4)^3)^2-1$
31438313	$9*(-8-7+(6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	32824278	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
31438315	$9*(-8-7+(6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	32824310	$-9+(8+7^6*(5+4))^3)^2-1$
31438439	$9*(8+7+(6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	32824328	$9+(8+7^6*(5+4))^3)^2-1$
31438441	$9*(-8+7+(6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	32826510	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
31438457	$9*(8-7+(6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	32827109	$(98+7^6*(5+4))^3)^2-1$
31438459	$9*(8-7+(6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	32829579	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
31438583	$9*(8+7+(6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	32829723	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
31438585	$9*(8+7+(6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	32839065	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
31438952	$9*(8*7+(6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	32839209	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
31438954	$9*(8*7+(6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	32998374	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
31439223	$9*(87+(6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	32998518	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
31439241	$9*(87+(6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	33029873	$9*(8^7-6*(5-4^3)^2)-1$
31606811	$9*(-8+(7-6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	33029875	$9*(8^7-6*(5-4^3)^2)+1$
31606813	$9*(-8+(7-6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	33030413	$9*(8^7+6*(5+4^3)^2)-1$
31606955	$9*(8+(7-6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	33030415	$9*(8^7+6*(5+4^3)^2)+1$
31606957	$9*(8+(7-6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	33073928	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4*3)^2)-1$
31664316	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4+3)/21)$	33073930	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4*3)^2)+1$
31664460	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4+3)/21)$	33074072	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4*3)^2)-1$
31674311	$9*(-8+(7-6+5^4*3)^2)-1$	33074074	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4*3)^2)+1$
31674313	$9*(-8+(7-6+5^4*3)^2)+1$	33202989	$(9+8)*(-7+(6-5+4)^3)^2-1$
31674455	$9*(8+(7-6+5^4*3)^2)-1$	33203023	$(9+8)*(-7+(6-5+4)^3)^2+1$
31674457	$9*(8+(7-6+5^4*3)^2)+1$	33203261	$(9+8)*(7+(6-5+4)^3)^2+1$
31719312	$9*(8*7+65)*(4^3)^2-1$	33347356	$9^8-7+6*5*(4^3)^2+1$
31719554	$9*(8*7+65)*(4^3)^2+1$	33347430	$9^8-(7+6*5)*(4^3)^2-1$
31764941	$9*(-8+(7^6*5-4)^3)^2-1$	33702831	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
31764943	$9*(-8+(7^6*5-4)^3)^2+1$	33702849	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
31764987	$(-9+8*7^6*5/4)^3(2+1)$	33702975	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
31765517	$9*(8+(7^6*5+4)^3)^2-1$	33702993	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
31765519	$9*(8+(7^6*5+4)^3)^2+1$	33765165	$-98+7^6*((5+4)^3)^2-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
33765361	$98+7^{\wedge}6*((5+4)*32-1)$	33984993	$9+87*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
33858360	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-321)$	33989064	$9*(87*(6+(5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$
33861240	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-321)$	33989082	$9*(87*(6+(5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$
33867279	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*32-1)$	34000510	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-3)-2-1)$
33867297	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*32+1)$	34000612	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4*3)+2+1)$
33867423	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*32-1)$	34062831	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*32-1)$
33867441	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*32+1)$	34062849	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*32+1)$
33877071	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)^*32-1)$	34062975	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*32-1)$
33877089	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)^*32+1)$	34062993	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*32+1)$
33878583	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-321)$	34164000	$9*(8/7+6)*(((5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
33879843	$9*((8*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-321)$	34257528	$9*(-8+(76+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
33880203	$9*((8*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-321)$	34257546	$9*(-8+(76+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
33880383	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*32-1)$	34257672	$9*(8+(76+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
33880401	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*32+1)$	34257690	$9*(8+(76+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
33881039	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3*2)-1$	34402998	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3-21)$
33881041	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3*2)+1$	34404762	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3-2-1)$
33881067	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3)-21)$	34404958	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3-2+1)$
33881175	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-32-1)$	34405007	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
33881193	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-32+1)$	34405105	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
33881310	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3-21)$	34405154	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3+2-1)$
33881417	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3*2)-1$	34405350	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3+2+1)$
33881419	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3*2)+1$	34407114	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3+21)$
33881525	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3*2)-1$	34572636	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3-2-1)$
33881527	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3*2)+1$	34572832	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3-2+1)$
33881634	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3+21)$	34572881	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
33881751	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+32-1)$	34572979	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
33881769	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+32+1)$	34573028	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3+2-1)$
33881877	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3)+21)$	34573224	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3+2+1)$
33881903	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3*2)-1$	34584102	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*3-21)$
33881905	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3*2)+1$	34584984	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*3+21)$
33882471	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)^*32-1)$	34586111	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
33882543	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^*32-1)$	34586209	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
33882561	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^*32+1)$	34588320	$(98*7^{\wedge}6-54*3)^*(2+1)$
33883353	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)^*32+1)$	34588561	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
33883919	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3*2)-1$	34588860	$(98*7^{\wedge}6+54/3)^*(2+1)$
33883921	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3*2)+1$	34589292	$(98*7^{\wedge}6+54*3)^*(2+1)$
33883947	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3)-21)$	34592628	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5*4)^*3-21)$
33884055	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-32-1)$	34593510	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*3+21)$
33884073	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-32+1)$	34594735	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5*4)^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
33884190	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3-21)$	34604388	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3-2-1)$
33884297	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3*2)-1$	34604584	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3-2+1)$
33884299	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3*2)+1$	34604633	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
33884405	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3*2)-1$	34604731	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
33884407	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3*2)+1$	34604780	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3+2-1)$
33884514	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3+21)$	34604976	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3+2+1)$
33884631	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+32-1)$	34700673	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4-3*21)$
33884649	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+32+1)$	34705992	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4-3*21)$
33884757	$9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3)+21)$	34706357	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-3*21)$
33884783	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3*2)-1$	34706553	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-3*21)$
33884785	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3*2)+1$	34706936	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4-3*21)$
33885423	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*32-1)$	34712237	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(-4+3*21)$
33885441	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*32+1)$	34756056	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*(32+1))$
33885621	$9*((8*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+321)$	34756200	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*(32+1))$
33885981	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+321)$	34770498	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3-21)$
33887241	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+321)$	34772262	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3-2-1)$
33888591	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)^*32-1)$	34772458	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3-2+1)$
33888609	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)^*32+1)$	34772507	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
33888753	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)^*32+1)$	34772605	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
33898383	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*32-1)$	34772654	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3+2-1)$
33898401	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*32+1)$	34772850	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3+2+1)$
33898527	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*32-1)$	34774614	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3+21)$
33898545	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*32+1)$	34857207	$9*((87+6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
33904584	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+321)$	34857225	$9*((87+6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
33979668	$9*(87*(-6+(5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$	34925643	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(32+1))$
33979686	$9*(87*(-6+(5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$	34925787	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(32+1))$
33983757	$-9-87*(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	34935741	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)^*(32+1))$
33983775	$9-87*(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	34935885	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)^*(32+1))$
33983931	$-9-87*(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	34938519	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))^*(32+1)$
33983949	$9-87*(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	34939008	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*(32+1))$
33984801	$-9+87*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	34939152	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*(32+1))$
33984819	$9+87*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	34941384	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^*(32+1))$
33984975	$-9+87*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	34941498	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))^*(32+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
34941528	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^*(32+1))$	36353443	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$
34941655	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^*(32+1)$	36353469	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$
34941851	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^*(32+1)$	36353613	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$
34941978	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^*(32+1))$	36353639	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$
34942008	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))^*(32+1)$	36391615	$(9*8-7)^*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)^2-1)$
34942026	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))^*(32+1)$	36391745	$(9*8-7)^*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)^2+1)$
34942122	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^*(32+1))$	36531552	$-9+87*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
34944354	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*(32+1))$	36531570	$9+87*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
34944987	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))^*(32+1)$	36531744	$9+87*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
34947621	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)^*(32+1))$	36543013	$(9+8)^*((7+6/5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
34947765	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)^*(32+1))$	36676868	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/21)$
34957719	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*(32+1))$	36706293	$9^*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4/3+2+1)$
34957863	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*(32+1))$	36710482	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/21)$
35046589	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	36824039	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
35127306	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*(32+1))$	36824065	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
35127450	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*(32+1))$	36824209	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
35156115	$9^*(8+7)^*(6*(5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	36824235	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
35156385	$9^*(8+7)^*(6*(5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	36885942	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
35176953	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	36897178	$9^{\wedge}8/(7/6)+5/(4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
35177149	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	36897183	$9^{\wedge}8/(7/6)-5/(4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
35281887	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	36897192	$9^{\wedge}8/(7/6)+(5+4)/(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
35296200	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+(3*2)^{\wedge}1-1)$	36903438	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
35311302	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	36907812	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
35380674	$-9*((8+7)^*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	36925308	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
35398206	$9*((8+7)^*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	37001214	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3))^*21)$
35398224	$9*((8+7)^*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	37001358	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3))^*21)$
35399211	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$	37017386	$9^{\wedge}8+(7-6*5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
35399861	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$	37017432	$9^{\wedge}8+(7-6*5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
35412332	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-321)$	37046601	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)-21$
35412348	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-321)$	37046643	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+21$
35412350	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-321)$	37057125	$(-98+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^3)*21$
35412366	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-321)$	37057629	$(-98+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^3)*21$
35634519	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	37058688	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^3*21$
35635149	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	37058912	$9*((-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4+3)-2)-1$
35643376	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*543)/(2+1)$	37058914	$9*((-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4+3)-2)+1$
35765224	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-321)$	37058948	$9*((-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4+3)+2)-1$
35765283	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	37058950	$9*((-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4+3)+2)+1$
35765291	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	37059024	$9-(8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^3)*21$
35765301	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	37059085	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^3*21$
35765309	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	37059192	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^3*21$
35765368	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-321)$	37059281	$98+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^3*21$
35861364	$-9*(8-76/5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	37059337	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
35869827	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	37059533	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
35870437	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	37059552	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3)+21)$
35871630	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)^*(4/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	37059589	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^3*21$
35872905	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)^*(4/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	37059785	$98+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^3*21$
35882847	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	37059864	$9+(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^3)*21$
35882873	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	37059920	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4+3)-2)-1$
35883017	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	37059922	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4+3)-2)+1$
35883043	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	37059956	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4+3)+2)-1$
35970054	$9*(87*(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	37059958	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4+3)+2)+1$
35970072	$9*(87*(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	37060128	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4+3)+21)$
35984070	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(3-21)$	37060200	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^3*21$
35987772	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5*4+3)^*(2+1)$	37061241	$(98+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^3)*21$
35987790	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5*4-3)^*(2+1)$	37061745	$(98+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^3)*21$
36000237	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54/3-21)$	37109280	$(-9+8*(7+6))^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
36000475	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)^2-1)$	37109470	$(-9+8*(7+6))^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
36000509	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)^2+1)$	37164231	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
36000679	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)^2-1)$	37164311	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
36000713	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)^2+1)$	37219126	$98*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
36000951	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54/3+21)$	37219322	$98*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
36017118	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*(3-21)$	37220106	$98*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
36096063	$9*(8*(7*6+5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2-1$	37220302	$98*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
36096065	$9*(8*(7*6+5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2+1$	37294635	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
36175734	$(9*8-7*6*5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	37294661	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
36176010	$(9*8-7*6*5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	37294805	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
36328023	$-9+(87+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	37294831	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
36328041	$9+(87+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	37399548	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)-21$
36328209	$-9+(87+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	37399590	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)+21$
36328227	$9+(87+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	37529933	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
36340707	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)-21$	37529959	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
36340749	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)+21$	37530103	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$

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37530129	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	39412343	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
37645990	$(-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	39412513	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3*21)$
37646170	$(9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	39528393	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43-2+1)$
37647390	$(-9+(8/7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	39530283	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-2+1)$
37647496	$(9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4))*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	39531753	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-2+1)$
37647561	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*4^{\wedge}3-21$	39638771	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6)*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
37647710	$(-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4+3))*2/1$	39638797	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6)*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
37647799	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*4^{\wedge}3+21$	39638901	$9^{\wedge}8+(7+6)*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
37647864	$(-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4))*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	39638927	$9^{\wedge}8+(7+6)*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
37649190	$(-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	39845727	$-9+(87+65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
37649370	$(9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	39845745	$9+(87+65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
37665838	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)/6+5)/4-3)^*21$	39846031	$-9+(87+65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
37665964	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)/6+5)/4+3)^*21$	39846049	$9+(87+65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
37745847	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)/4-321)$	39869658	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
37751625	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)/4+321)$	39870189	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)^*(2+1)$
37758892	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)^*321$	39870207	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)^*(2+1)$
37758908	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)^*321$	39870738	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
37758910	$9-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)^*321$	39995203	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4-321)$
37758926	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)^*321$	39998943	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4*(3+2))-1$
37771732	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)^*321$	39998951	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$
37771748	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)^*321$	39998969	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$
37771750	$9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)^*321$	39998977	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4*(3+2)+1)$
37771766	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)^*321$	40000201	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
37968583	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	40000524	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4-3^{\wedge}2+1)$
37968609	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	40000541	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4-3*2-1)$
37968993	$9^{\wedge}(8+7)/6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)^*2+1)$	40000557	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4-3*2)-1$
38000529	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(54*3*2-1)$	40000763	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4+3*2)+1$
38000725	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(54*3*2-1)$	40000779	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4+3*2+1)$
38118141	$9*((-8+7^{\wedge}6*54/3)^*2+1)$	40000796	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$
38118411	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*54/3)^*2-1)$	40001119	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
38118429	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*54/3)^*2+1)$	40002343	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4*(3+2))-1$
38235827	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(54*3*2+1)$	40002369	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$
38236023	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(54*3*2+1)$	40002377	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4*(3+2)+1)$
38258649	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(54^{\wedge}3-21)$	40006117	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4+321)$
38268855	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(54^{\wedge}3+21)$	40105371	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4*3*2+1)$
38279878	$98*(-7-6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	40105621	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3*2+1)$
38280074	$98*(-7-6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	40221849	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*(3+21)$
38281054	$98*(-7+6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	40224441	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(3+21)$
38282426	$98*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	40235697	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)+21)$
38282622	$98*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	40235859	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)+2+1)$
38285268	$98*(7*6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	40235865	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))-21$
38285464	$98*(7*6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	40235877	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)+2-1)$
38328111	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	40235895	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)-2+1)$
38328147	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	40235907	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))+21$
38340729	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	40235913	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)-2-1)$
38340793	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	40236009	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))-21$
38371606	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2-1)$	40236051	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))+21$
38371802	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2+1)$	40236075	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)-21)$
38499948	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	40236219	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)+21)$
38576038	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)-21$	40310279	$9*8*(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)^*2)-1$
38576080	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)+21$	40310281	$9*8*(-7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)^*2)+1$
38587231	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43-2)+1)$	40311287	$9*8*(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)^*2)-1$
38587233	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43-2)-1)$	40311289	$9*8*(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)^*2)+1$
38587249	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43-2)+1)$	40335085	$98*(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
38590513	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-2)-1)$	40340679	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4*3*2-1)$
38590529	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-2)+1)$	40340909	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3*2-1)$
38706423	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$	40353418	$(98*7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
38706449	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$	40353796	$(98*7^{\wedge}6+54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
38706593	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$	40372129	$98*(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
38706619	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$	40469521	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43-2-1)$
38941721	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	40469523	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43-2^{\wedge}-1)$
38941747	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	40469531	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$
38941891	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	40469535	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43+2-1)$
38941917	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	40469537	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43-2+1)$
39162522	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*(32+1)$	40469541	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43-2^{\wedge}-1)$
39166086	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(32+1)$	40469549	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$
39303928	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)-3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	40469551	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43+2+1)$
39397928	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*(32-1)$	40469553	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43+2-1)$
39399447	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	40469569	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43+2+1)$
39399757	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	40472961	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43-2-1)$
39401276	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(32-1)$	40472971	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$
39412317	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3*21)$	40472977	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43-2+1)$

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40472981	$9+8*((7^6+5)*43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	41870241	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*((3^{\wedge}2+1)$
40472989	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	41870321	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*((3^{\wedge}2+1)$
40472991	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*43+2+1)$	41870431	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)*((3^{\wedge}2+1)$
40472993	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*43+2-1)$	41923938	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6-5*43)*21$
40473009	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*43+2+1)$	41980344	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6-54-3)*21$
40575714	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)*21$	41982486	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6-54+3)*21$
40576470	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-54/3)*21$	41983557	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6-5-43)*21$
40693725	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*(3+2-1)$	41987127	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5-43)*21$
40693757	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*(3+2-1)$	41994267	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6-54/3)*21$
40781113	$9+8/76*((5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	41998635	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-3))*21$
40811295	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$	42000534	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-3))*21$
40811485	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$	42000595	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-3)*21$
40897132	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6/5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	42000791	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-3)*21$
40928067	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(3-21)$	42000870	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-3))*21$
40929018	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*54/3-21$	42002751	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-3))*21$
40929060	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*54/3+21$	42007119	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)*21$
40930011	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3-21)$	42007707	$(-9+8*(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$
40940103	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	42008085	$(9+8*(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$
40940121	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	42014259	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6-5+43)*21$
40943583	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	42017829	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5+43)*21$
40943601	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	42018900	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+54-3)*21$
40949561	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	42021042	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+54+3)*21$
40949577	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	42058527	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+54*3)*21$
41149808	$98*(-7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	42077448	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5*43)*21$
41150004	$98*(-7+(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	42105369	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)*((3^{\wedge}2-1)$
41162445	$9/8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1)$	42105457	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*((3^{\wedge}2-1)$
41281794	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3)*(2+1)$	42105519	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*((3^{\wedge}2-1)$
41281911	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4*3+2+1)$	42105521	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*((3^{\wedge}2-1)$
41281950	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4*3)*(2+1)$	42105537	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*((3^{\wedge}2-1)$
41281965	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4+3)*(2+1)$	42105539	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*((3^{\wedge}2-1)$
41281982	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4/3)*(2+1)$	42105601	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*((3^{\wedge}2-1)$
41281983	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4-3)*(2+1)$	42105689	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)*((3^{\wedge}2-1)$
41281989	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4+3)*(2+1)$	42205023	$(9+87+65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
41281990	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4/3)*(2+1)$	42205345	$(9+87+65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
41282007	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4-3)*(2+1)$	42220503	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-43^{\wedge}2)-1)$
41282022	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4*3)*(2+1)$	42220521	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-43^{\wedge}2)+1)$
41282061	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3+2+1)$	42252624	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
41282178	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3)*(2+1)$	42260292	$9/8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*321$
41317047	$9^{\wedge}8*7-(6*5)^{\wedge}4*321$	42316775	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
41410679	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2-1)$	42316777	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
41410697	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2-1)$	42322464	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-432-1)$
41412237	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2-1)$	42322527	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-432)-1)$
41412677	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2-1)$	42322545	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-432)+1)$
41414217	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2-1)$	42322608	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-432+1)$
41421664	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	42324020	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4/(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$
41421808	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	42330240	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4-321)$
41473851	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	42330816	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4-321)$
41473863	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	42334128	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*((3+2)-1)$
41508178	$-9+8*7/(6/543)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	42334191	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*((3+2)-1)$
41508196	$9+8*7/(6/543)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	42334209	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*((3+2)+1)$
41511447	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7-6)/(5+4))^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	42334272	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*((3+2)+1)$
41526280	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-6/5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	42336990	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6-6*5-43^{\wedge}2-1)$
41526645	$9^{\wedge}8-76*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	42337008	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6-6*5-43^{\wedge}2+1)$
41526797	$9^{\wedge}8-76*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	42341544	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6-6*5-4^{\wedge}3*21)$
41546439	$9^{\wedge}8*((7^{\wedge}(-6+5)-4)^{\wedge}-3*2+1)$	42342084	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6-6*5-4*321)$
41576046	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	42345513	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6-6*5-43*21)$
41576171	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	42348843	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3)-21)$
41634864	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4+3*(2+1)$	42349221	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3)+21)$
41634882	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4-3*(2+1)$	42349743	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*5-432-1)$
41634984	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4+3*(2+1)$	42349761	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*5-432+1)$
41635002	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4-3*(2+1)$	42350355	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-43)-21)$
41642304	$9^{\wedge}8-7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*321)$	42350463	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)-321)$
41642388	$9^{\wedge}8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*321)$	42350517	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-43)-2-1)$
41693700	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	42350523	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-43)-21$
41693815	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	42350535	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-43)-2+1)$
41752527	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+3*2+1)$	42350565	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-43)+21$
41752637	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4+3*2+1)$	42350571	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-43)+2+1)$
41870031	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)*((3^{\wedge}2+1)$	42350679	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-43+2)-1)$
41870141	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*((3^{\wedge}2+1)$	42350733	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-43)+21)$
41870221	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*((3^{\wedge}2+1)$	42350787	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*5+4-321)$
41870223	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*(3-2+1)$	42351615	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4-32)-1)$
41870239	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*(3-2+1)$	42351633	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4-32)+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
42351823	$-9+8*((7^6-5)*(43+2)-1)$	42373071	$9*(8*(7^6+54)*(3+2)-1)$
42351857	$9+8*((7^6-5)*(43+2)+1)$	42373089	$9*(8*(7^6+54)*(3+2)+1)$
42351876	$(98-7^6*5^4)*(3-21)$	42373152	$9*8*((7^6+54)*(3+2)+1)$
42351911	$9*8*(7^6*5-4*3^2)-1$	42376464	$9*8*(7^6*5-4+321)$
42351913	$9*8*(7^6*5-4*3^2)+1$	42377040	$9*8*(7^6*5+4+321)$
42352083	$9*(8*(7^6*5-43/2)-1)$	42384672	$9*8*(7^6*5+432-1)$
42352101	$9*(8*(7^6*5-43/2)+1)$	42384735	$9*(8*(7^6*5+432)-1)$
42352199	$9*8*(7^6*5-4*(3+2))-1$	42384753	$9*(8*(7^6*5+432)+1)$
42352201	$9*8*(7^6*5-4*(3+2))+1$	42384816	$9*8*(7^6*5+432+1)$
42352343	$9*(8/(7^6-6/5)-(4*3)^2)-1$	42393111	$9^8-(7^6*5+4)*(3^6-2+1)$
42352345	$9*(8/(7^6-6/5)-(4*3)^2)+1$	42446471	$9^8-7^6*5*((4+3)^{-2}+1)$
42352631	$9*8*(7^6*5-4*3^2)-1$	42467255	$9*(-8+(7+6+5)^4*3^2)-1$
42352633	$9*8*(7^6*5-4*3^2)+1$	42467257	$9*(-8+(7+6+5)^4*3^2)+1$
42352757	$9*(8*(7^6*5-4*3^2)-1)$	42470481	$9^8+7^6*5*((4+3)^{-2}-1)$
42352759	$9*(8*(7^6*5-4*3^2)+1)$	42482745	$9/8*(7^6-5-4)^*321$
42352793	$9*(8*(7^6*5-4*3^2)+2)-1$	42485634	$9/8*(7^6-5+4)^*321$
42352795	$9*(8*(7^6*5-4*3^2)+2)+1$	42486759	$9*(8*(7^6*5+43^2)-1)$
42352919	$9*8*(7^6*5-4*3+2)-1$	42486777	$9*(8*(7^6*5+43^2)+1)$
42352921	$9*8*(7^6*5-4*3+2)+1$	42497669	$9^8-(7^6+5)*(4+(3/2)^{-1})$
42352947	$9*(8*(7^6*5-4-3)-21)$	42523833	$9^8+(7^6*5+4)*(3^6-2-1)$
42353031	$9*8*(7^6*5-4)-321$	42536887	$9^8-(7^6+5)*(4/3+2+1)$
42353232	$9*(8*7^6*5-43)-21$	42556496	$9^8-(7^6+5)*4+(3^2)^{-1}$
42353274	$9*(8*7^6*5-43)+21$	42573625	$9^8-(7^6+5^4)*(3+2-1)$
42353283	$9*(8*7^6*5-4)-321$	42576045	$9^8-(7^6+5*4)*(3+2-1)$
42353299	$9*(8*(7^6*5-4)-3^2)+1$	42576089	$9^8-(7^6+5+4)*(3+2-1)$
42353981	$9*(8*(7^6*5+4)+3^2)-1$	42576120	$9^8-(7^6+5/4)*(3+2-1)$
42353997	$9*(8*7^6*5+4)+321$	42576130	$9^8-(7^6-5/4)*(3+2-1)$
42354006	$9*(8*7^6*5+43)-21$	42576161	$9^8-(7^6-5-4)*(3+2-1)$
42354048	$9*(8*7^6*5+43)+21$	42576205	$9^8-(7^6-5*4)*(3+2-1)$
42354249	$9*8*(7^6*5+4)+321$	42578625	$9^8-(7^6-5^4)*(3+2-1)$
42354333	$9*(8*(7^6*5+4+3)+21)$	42595714	$9^8-(7^6+5)*(4-(3^2)^{-1})$
42354359	$9*8*(7^6*5+4*3^2)-1$	42609739	$9^8-7^6*(5/(4+3)+2+1)$
42354361	$9*8*(7^6*5+4*3^2)+1$	42615323	$9^8-(7^6+5)*(4/3+2+1)$
42354485	$9*(8*(7^6*5+4*3^2)-1)$	42634918	$9^8-(7^6+5+4)*(3+2^6-1)$
42354487	$9*(8*(7^6*5+4*3^2)+1)$	42634946	$9^8-(7^6+5-4)*(3+2^6-1)$
42354521	$9*(8*(7^6*5+4*3^2)+2)-1$	42634953	$9^8-(7^6-5+4)*(3+2^6-1)$
42354523	$9*(8*(7^6*5+4*3^2)+2)+1$	42634981	$9^8-(7^6-5-4)*(3+2^6-1)$
42354647	$9*8*(7^6*5+4*3+2)-1$	42669774	$9^8-(7^6+(5^4)^3)*(2+1)$
42354649	$9*8*(7^6*5+4*3+2)+1$	42688149	$9^8-(7^6+5^4*3)*(2+1)$
42354935	$9*(8/(7^6-6/5)+(4*3)^2)-1$	42691890	$9^8-(7^6+5^4+3)*(2+1)$
42354937	$9*(8/(7^6-6/5)+(4*3)^2)+1$	42691908	$9^8-(7^6+5^4-3)*(2+1)$
42355079	$9*(8*(7^6*5+4*(3+2))-1)$	42692145	$9^8-(7^6+5^4)^*(2+1)$
42355081	$9*8*(7^6*5+4*(3+2))+1$	42692814	$9^8-(7^6+5^4*3)^*(2+1)$
42355179	$9*(8*(7^6*5+43/2)-1)$	42693149	$9^8-(7^6+5^4/3)^*(2+1)$
42355197	$9*(8*(7^6*5+43/2)+1)$	42693567	$9^8-(7^6+5+4^3)^*(2+1)$
42355367	$9*8*(7^6*5+4*3^2)-1$	42693594	$9^8-(7^6+5*4^3)^*(2+1)$
42355369	$9*8*(7^6*5+4*3^2)+1$	42693597	$9^8-(7^6-5+4^3)^*(2+1)$
42355404	$(98+7^6*5^4)*(-3+21)$	42693669	$9^8-(7^6+5*(4+3))^*(2+1)$
42355457	$9+8*((7^6+5)*(43+2)+1)$	42693705	$9^8-(7^6+5*4+3)^*(2+1)$
42355647	$9*(8*(7^6*5-4+32)-1)$	42693723	$9^8-(7^6+5+4^3)^*(2+1)$
42355665	$9*(8*(7^6*5-4+32)+1)$	42693738	$9^8-(7^6+5+4+3)^*(2+1)$
42356079	$9*((8*7^6+54)*(3+2)+1)$	42693754	$9^8-(7^6+5*4/3)^*(2+1)$
42356493	$9*(8*7^6*5-4+321)$	42693755	$9^8-(7^6+5+4/3)^*(2+1)$
42356547	$9*(8*(7^6*5+43)-21)$	42693762	$9^8-(7^6+5-4+3)^*(2+1)$
42356601	$9*(8*(7^6*5+43-2)+1)$	42693763	$9^8-(7^6+5-4/3)^*(2+1)$
42356709	$9*(8*(7^6*5+43)-2-1)$	42693765	$9^8-(7^6+(5+4)/3)^*(2+1)$
42356715	$9*8*(7^6*5+43)-21$	42693783	$9^8-(7^6-(5+4)/3)^*(2+1)$
42356745	$9*(8*(7^6*5+43)+2-1)$	42693785	$9^8-(7^6-5+4/3)^*(2+1)$
42356757	$9*8*(7^6*5+43)+21$	42693786	$9^8-(7^6-5+4-3)^*(2+1)$
42356763	$9*(8*(7^6*5+43)+2+1)$	42693793	$9^8-(7^6-5-4/3)^*(2+1)$
42356925	$9*(8*(7^6*5+43)+21)$	42693794	$9^8-(7^6-5*4/3)^*(2+1)$
42357519	$9*(8*7^6*5+432-1)$	42693810	$9^8-(7^6-5-4-3)^*(2+1)$
42357537	$9*(8*7^6*5+432+1)$	42693825	$9^8-(7^6-5-4*3)^*(2+1)$
42358059	$9*(8*(7^6*5+4^3)-21)$	42693843	$9^8-(7^6-5*4-3)^*(2+1)$
42358437	$9*(8*(7^6*5+4^3)+21)$	42693879	$9^8-(7^6-5*(4+3))^*(2+1)$
42361767	$9*(8/7^6-6*5+4^3*21)$	42693951	$9^8-(7^6+5-4^3)^*(2+1)$
42365144	$9^8-(7+6)/5*(4^3+2+1)$	42693954	$9^8-(7^6-5*4^3)^*(2+1)$
42365196	$9*(8/7^6-6*5+4^3*21)$	42693981	$9^8-(7^6-5-4^3)^*(2+1)$
42365736	$9*(8/7^6-6*5+4^3*21)$	42694399	$9^8-(7^6-5^4/3)^*(2+1)$
42370272	$9*(8*7^6*5+43^2-1)$	42694734	$9^8-(7^6-5*4^3)^*(2+1)$
42370290	$9*(8*7^6*5+43^2+1)$	42695403	$9^8-(7^6-5^4)^*(2+1)$
42373008	$9*8*((7^6+54)*(3+2)-1)$	42695640	$9^8-(7^6-5^4+3)^*(2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
42695658	$9^8 - (7^6 - 5^4 - 3)^*(2+1)$	43055296	$9^8 + (7^6/5^4 - 4)^{(3/2-1)}$
42699399	$9^8 - (7^6 - 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	43062880	$9^8 + (7+6)^*((5^4-3)^*2-1)$
42706587	$9^8 * 7^6 * (5 + (4^3 * 2)^{-1})$	43062906	$9^8 + (7+6)^*((5^4-3)^*2+1)$
42717774	$9^8 - (7^6 - (5^4)^3)^*(2+1)$	43063036	$9^8 + (7+6)^*((5^4+3)^*2-1)$
42740891	$9^8 + 7/6 * (5 - 4^3)^{2-1}$	43066020	$9^8 - 76 + 5^4 * (32-1)$
42751036	$9^8 - (7^6 + 5^4)^*(3/2+1)$	43066172	$9^8 + 76 + 5^4 * (32-1)$
42754161	$9^8 - (7^6 - 5^4)^*(3/2+1)$	43067270	$9^8 - 76 + 5^4 * (32+1)$
42772195	$9^8 - (7^6 + 5)^*(4/3+2-1)$	43067422	$9^8 + 76 + 5^4 * (32+1)$
42794616	$9^8 - 7^6 * 5 / (4/3+2-1)$	43068508	$9^8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4) / 3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
42831022	$9^8 - (7^6 + 5)^*(4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	43070979	$9^8 + (7+6)^*(5^4-3)^*(2+1)$
42850618	$9^8 - (7^6 * 5 + 4^3) / (2+1)$	43071083	$9^8 + (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3 - 2 + 1)$
42850631	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5)^*(4/3-2-1)$	43071087	$9^8 + ((7+6)^*5^4 - 3)^*(2+1)$
42869047	$9^8 - 7^6 * ((5 / (4+3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	43071105	$9^8 + ((7+6)^*5^4 + 3)^*(2+1)$
42902625	$9^8 - 7^6 * (5^4 * 3 + 21)$	43071109	$9^8 + (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3 + 2 - 1)$
42908933	$9^8 + 7 * ((6 - 5 - 4)^3)^{2-1}$	43071135	$9^8 + (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3 + 2 + 1)$
42908947	$9^8 + 7 * ((6 - 5 - 4)^3)^{2+1}$	43071213	$9^8 + (7+6)^*(5^4 + 3)^*(2+1)$
42916001	$9^8 - (7^6 - 5 + 4)^*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	43072880	$9^8 - 7 * ((6 - 5^4 * 3)^*2 + 1)$
42917067	$9^8 - 7^6 * (5 / (4+3))^{\wedge}2 + 1$	43072894	$9^8 - 7 * ((6 - 5^4 * 3)^*2 - 1)$
42922062	$9^8 * (-76 / (5^4 * 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1$	43073048	$9^8 + 7 * ((6 + 5^4 * 3)^*2 - 1)$
42941077	$9^8 + 7^6 * (5 / (4+3))^{\wedge}2 - 1$	43073062	$9^8 + 7 * ((6 + 5^4 * 3)^*2 + 1)$
42942143	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5/4)^*(3^{\wedge}-2-1)$	43075811	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5) / 4 - 321$
42942145	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 + 4)^*(3^{\wedge}-2-1)$	43076453	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5) / 4 + 321$
42948676	$9^8 - (7^6 + 5)^*(4/3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	43080450	$9^8 - (7 - 6 * 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$
42958479	$9^8 - ((7^6 - 5) / 4 + 3)^*(2+1)$	43080492	$9^8 + (7 + 6 * 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$
42958497	$9^8 - ((7^6 - 5) / 4 - 3)^*(2+1)$	43095458	$9^8 + (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3^2 - 1)$
42967908	$9^8 - 7 * (6 * 5^4 + 3)^*(2+1)$	43095484	$9^8 + (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3^2 + 1)$
42967962	$9^8 - (7 * 6 * 5^4 + 3)^*(2+1)$	43099150	$9^8 + (7 - 6) / 5 * (4^3)^{2+1}$
42968034	$9^8 - 7 * (6 * 5^4 - 3)^*(2+1)$	43099172	$9^8 + 7 * ((6 * 5^4 - 3)^*2 - 1)$
42973583	$9^8 - (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3^2 + 1)$	43099186	$9^8 + 7 * ((6 * 5^4 - 3)^*2 + 1)$
42973609	$9^8 - (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3^2 - 1)$	43099256	$9^8 + 7 * ((6 * 5^4 + 3)^*2 - 1)$
42994172	$9^8 - 7 * ((6 * 5^4 + 3)^*2 + 1)$	43099270	$9^8 + 7 * ((6 * 5^4 + 3)^*2 + 1)$
42994186	$9^8 - 7 * ((6 * 5^4 + 3)^*2 - 1)$	43119833	$9^8 + (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3^2 - 1)$
42994256	$9^8 - 7 * ((6 * 5^4 - 3)^*2 + 1)$	43119859	$9^8 + (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3^2 + 1)$
42994270	$9^8 - 7 * ((6 * 5^4 - 3)^*2 - 1)$	43125408	$9^8 + 7 * (6 * 5^4 - 3)^*(2+1)$
42994292	$9^8 - (7 - 6) / 5 * (4^3)^{2+1}$	43125534	$9^8 + 7 * (6 * 5^4 + 3)^*(2+1)$
42997958	$9^8 - (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3^2 + 1)$	43134945	$9^8 + ((7^6 - 5) / 4 - 3)^*(2+1)$
42997984	$9^8 - (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3^2 - 1)$	43134963	$9^8 + ((7^6 - 5) / 4 + 3)^*(2+1)$
43005168	$9^8 * (-76 / 5^4 * 3^2 + 1)$	43144766	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5)^*(4/3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
43012950	$9^8 - (7 + 6 * 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	43151297	$9^8 - (7^6 - 5 + 4)^*(3^{\wedge} - 2 - 1)$
43012992	$9^8 + (7 - 6 * 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	43151299	$9^8 - (7^6 + 5/4)^*(3^{\wedge} - 2 - 1)$
43016989	$9^8 - (7^6 - 5) / 4 - 321$	43152365	$9^8 - 7^6 * (5 / (4+3))^{\wedge}2 - 1$
43017631	$9^8 - (7^6 - 5) / 4 + 321$	43171380	$9^8 * (76 / (5^4 * 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1$
43020380	$9^8 - 7 * ((6 + 5^4 * 3)^*2 + 1)$	43176375	$9^8 + 7^6 * (5 / (4+3))^{\wedge}2 + 1$
43020394	$9^8 - 7 * ((6 + 5^4 * 3)^*2 - 1)$	43177441	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 + 4)^*(3^{\wedge} - 2 + 1)$
43020548	$9^8 + 7 * ((6 - 5^4 * 3)^*2 - 1)$	43184495	$9^8 - 7 * ((6 - 5 - 4)^3)^{2+1}$
43020562	$9^8 + 7 * ((6 - 5^4 * 3)^*2 + 1)$	43184509	$9^8 - 7 * ((6 - 5 - 4)^3)^{2-1}$
43022229	$9^8 - (7+6)^*(5^4 + 3)^*(2+1)$	43190817	$9^8 + 76 * (5^4 * 3 + 21)$
43022307	$9^8 - (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3 + 2 + 1)$	43224395	$9^8 + 7^6 * ((5 / (4+3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
43022333	$9^8 - (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3 + 2 - 1)$	43242811	$9^8 - (7^6 + 5)^*(4/3 - 2 - 1)$
43022337	$9^8 - ((7+6)^*5^4 + 3)^*(2+1)$	43242824	$9^8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4^3) / (2+1)$
43022355	$9^8 - ((7+6)^*5^4 - 3)^*(2+1)$	43262420	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5)^*(4/3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
43022359	$9^8 - (7+6)^*(5^4 * 3 - 2 + 1)$	43292983	$-9 + 8 * (7^6 - 5)^*(43 + 2 + 1)$
43022463	$9^8 - (7+6)^*(5^4 - 3)^*(2+1)$	43293001	$9 + 8 * (7^6 - 5)^*(43 + 2 + 1)$
43024934	$9^8 - (7^6 * 5 + 4) / 3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	43294611	$9 + (8 * 7^6 - 5)^*(43 + 2 + 1)$
43026020	$9^8 - 76 - 5^4 * (32 + 1)$	43295071	$9 + (8 * 7^6 + 5)^*(43 + 2 + 1)$
43026172	$9^8 + 76 - 5^4 * (32 + 1)$	43296663	$-9 + 8 * (7^6 + 5)^*(43 + 2 + 1)$
43027270	$9^8 - 76 - 5^4 * (32 - 1)$	43296681	$9 + 8 * (7^6 + 5)^*(43 + 2 + 1)$
43027422	$9^8 + 76 - 5^4 * (32 - 1)$	43298826	$9^8 + 7^6 * 5 / (4/3 + 2 - 1)$
43030406	$9^8 - (7+6)^*((5^4 + 3)^*2 - 1)$	43321247	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5)^*(4/3 + 2 - 1)$
43030536	$9^8 - (7+6)^*((5^4 - 3)^*2 + 1)$	43339281	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5^4)^*(3/2 + 1)$
43030562	$9^8 - (7+6)^*((5^4 - 3)^*2 - 1)$	43342406	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5^4)^*(3/2 + 1)$
43038146	$9^8 - (7^6 / 5^4 - 4)^{(3/2-1)}$	43348830	$(-98 + 7^6 / 5)^*(43^2 + 1)$
43040750	$9^8 - (76 + 5^4 / 3)^*21$	43352551	$9^8 - 7/6 * (5 - 4^3)^{2-1}$
43040970	$9^8 - (7^6 + 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	43375668	$9^8 + (7^6 - (5^4)^3)^*(2+1)$
43041057	$9^8 - (7^6 + 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	43394043	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$
43041099	$9^8 + (7 - 6 - 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	43397784	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5^4 - 3)^*(2+1)$
43041222	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	43397802	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5^4 + 3)^*(2+1)$
43052220	$9^8 - (7^6 - 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	43398039	$9^8 + (7^6 - 543)^*(2+1)$
43052343	$9^8 - (7 - 6 - 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	43398708	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$
43052385	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	43399043	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5^4 / 3)^*(2+1)$
43052472	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	43399461	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 - 4^3)^*(2+1)$
43052692	$9^8 + (76 + 5^4 / 3)^*21$	43399488	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
43399491	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 - 4^3) * (2+1)$	43987905	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 + 4) * (3^2 - 1)$
43399563	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 * (4+3)) * (2+1)$	43987921	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 - 4) * (3^2 - 1)$
43399599	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 * 4 - 3) * (2+1)$	43987923	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5/4) * (3^2 - 1)$
43399617	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 - 4 * 3) * (2+1)$	43987985	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 + 4) * (3^2 - 1)$
43399632	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 - 4 - 3) * (2+1)$	43988073	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 * 4) * (3^2 - 1)$
43399648	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 * 4/3) * (2+1)$	44000682	$-9 + (8^7 - 6 - 5^4 * 3) * 21$
43399649	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 - 4/3) * (2+1)$	44000700	$9 + (8^7 - 6 - 5^4 * 3) * 21$
43399656	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 + 4 - 3) * (2+1)$	44000709	$(9+8) * (7^6 * (54 - 32) - 1)$
43399657	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 + 4/3) * (2+1)$	44000743	$(9+8) * (7^6 * (54 - 32) + 1)$
43399659	$9^8 + (7^6 - (5+4)/3) * (2+1)$	44000934	$-9 + (8^7 + 6 - 5^4 * 3) * 21$
43399677	$9^8 + (7^6 + (5+4)/3) * (2+1)$	44000952	$9 + (8^7 + 6 - 5^4 * 3) * 21$
43399679	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 - 4/3) * (2+1)$	44013933	$-9 + (8^7 - 6 * 5^4/3) * 21$
43399680	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 - 4 + 3) * (2+1)$	44013951	$9 + (8^7 - 6 * 5^4/3) * 21$
43399687	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 + 4/3) * (2+1)$	44035682	$-9 + (8^7 - 6 - 5^4/3) * 21$
43399688	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 * 4/3) * (2+1)$	44035700	$9 + (8^7 - 6 - 5^4/3) * 21$
43399704	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 + 4 + 3) * (2+1)$	44035934	$-9 + (8^7 + 6 - 5^4/3) * 21$
43399719	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 + 4 * 3) * (2+1)$	44035952	$9 + (8^7 + 6 - 5^4/3) * 21$
43399737	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 * 4 + 3) * (2+1)$	44044432	$-9 + (8^7 - 6 + 5^4/3) * 21$
43399773	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 * (4+3)) * (2+1)$	44044450	$9 + (8^7 - 6 + 5^4/3) * 21$
43399845	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 + 4^3) * (2+1)$	44044684	$-9 + (8^7 + 6 + 5^4/3) * 21$
43399848	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 * 4 * 3) * (2+1)$	44044702	$9 + (8^7 + 6 + 5^4/3) * 21$
43399875	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 + 4^3) * (2+1)$	44066433	$-9 + (8^7 + 6 * 5^4/3) * 21$
43400293	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5^4/3) * (2+1)$	44066451	$9 + (8^7 + 6 * 5^4/3) * 21$
43400628	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 * 4^3) * (2+1)$	44079432	$-9 + (8^7 - 6 + 5^4 * 3) * 21$
43401297	$9^8 + (7^6 + 543) * (2+1)$	44079450	$9 + (8^7 - 6 + 5^4 * 3) * 21$
43401534	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5^4 - 3) * (2+1)$	44079684	$-9 + (8^7 + 6 + 5^4 * 3) * 21$
43401552	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5^4 + 3) * (2+1)$	44079702	$9 + (8^7 + 6 + 5^4 * 3) * 21$
43405293	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5^4 * 3) * (2+1)$	44223011	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 * 4) * (3^2 + 1)$
43410555	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 - 5) * (43 - 2) - 1)$	44223121	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 - 4) * (3^2 + 1)$
43410573	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 - 5) * (43 - 2) + 1)$	44223201	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 + 4) * (3^2 + 1)$
43410717	$9 * (8 + (7^6 - 5) * (43 - 2) + 1)$	44223203	$9^8 + (7^6 * 5 - 4) * (3 - 2 + 1)$
43414245	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 + 5) * (43 - 2) - 1)$	44223219	$9^8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4) * (3 - 2 + 1)$
43414263	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 + 5) * (43 - 2) + 1)$	44223221	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 - 4) * (3^2 + 1)$
43423668	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 * 4^3) * (2+1)$	44223301	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 + 4) * (3^2 + 1)$
43458461	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 - 4) * (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	44223411	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 * 4) * (3^2 + 1)$
43458489	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 + 4) * (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	44229809	$(9 * 8 + 7) * (6^{\wedge} (-5 + 4 * 3) * 2 - 1)$
43458496	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 - 4) * (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	44229967	$(9 * 8 + 7) * (6^{\wedge} (-5 + 4 * 3) * 2 + 1)$
43458524	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 + 4) * (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	44276433	$-9 + (8^7 + 6 * 5^4 * 3) * 21$
43478119	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4/3 * 2 + 1)$	44276451	$9 + (8^7 + 6 * 5^4 * 3) * 21$
43483703	$9^8 + 7^6 * (5/(4+3) + 2 + 1)$	44340805	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5) * (4 + 3 * 2 + 1)$
43497728	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4 - (3 * 2)^{\wedge} - 1)$	44340915	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4 + 3 * 2 + 1)$
43514817	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5^4) * (3 + 2 - 1)$	44399627	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5) * (4 * 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
43515321	$-9 - (8 - 7^6/5) * (43^2 + 1)$	44399742	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4 * 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
43515339	$9 - (8 - 7^6/5) * (43^2 + 1)$	44451054	$9^8 - 7 * (6 - 5^4 * 321)$
43517237	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 * 4) * (3 + 2 - 1)$	44451138	$9^8 + 7 * (6 + 5^4 * 321)$
43517281	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 - 4) * (3 + 2 - 1)$	44458440	$9^8 + ((7^6 - 5) * 4 - 3) * (2 + 1)$
43517312	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5/4) * (3 + 2 - 1)$	44458458	$9^8 + ((7^6 - 5) * 4 + 3) * (2 + 1)$
43517322	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5/4) * (3 + 2 - 1)$	44458560	$9^8 + ((7^6 + 5) * 4 - 3) * (2 + 1)$
43517353	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 + 4) * (3 + 2 - 1)$	44458578	$9^8 + ((7^6 + 5) * 4 + 3) * (2 + 1)$
43517397	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5 * 4) * (3 + 2 - 1)$	44469360	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 - 5) * (43 - 2 + 1))$
43519817	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5^4) * (3 + 2 - 1)$	44469504	$9 * (8 + (7^6 - 5) * (43 - 2 + 1))$
43530032	$-98 + 7^6/5 * (43^2 + 1)$	44470965	$(-9 - 8 + 7^6 * 54/3) * 21$
43530228	$98 + 7^6/5 * (43^2 + 1)$	44471077	$(9 + (8 - 7^6 * 54)/3) * -21$
43536946	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4 + (3 * 2)^{\wedge} - 1)$	44471145	$-9 - (8 - 7^6 * 54/3) * 21$
43544921	$-9 + (8 + 7^6/5) * (43^2 + 1)$	44471163	$9 - (8 - 7^6 * 54/3) * 21$
43544939	$9 + (8 + 7^6/5) * (43^2 + 1)$	44471189	$(-9 + (8 + 7^6 * 54)/3) * 21$
43556555	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4/3 + 2 + 1)$	44471205	$9 - (8 - 7^6 * 54) / 3 * 21$
43568499	$(-9 + 876/5) * (4^3 + 2 + 1)$	44471301	$(-9 + 8 + 7^6 * 54/3) * 21$
43569609	$9^8 - (7^6 * 5 + 4) * (3^{\wedge} - 2 - 1)$	44471343	$(9 - 8 + 7^6 * 54/3) * 21$
43595773	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4 + (3/2)^{\wedge} - 1)$	44471387	$9 + (8 + 7^6 * 54) / 3 * 21$
43622961	$9^8 - 7^6 * 5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} - 2 - 1)$	44471455	$(9 - (8 - 7^6 * 54)/3) * 21$
43646971	$9^8 + 7^6 * 5 * ((4+3)^{\wedge} - 2 + 1)$	44471481	$-9 + (8 + 7^6 * 54/3) * 21$
43700331	$9^8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4) * (3^{\wedge} - 2 + 1)$	44471499	$9 + (8 + 7^6 * 54/3) * 21$
43711430	$(98 + 7^6/5) * (43^2 + 1)$	44471567	$(9 + (8 + 7^6 * 54)/3) * 21$
43728298	$9^8 + (7 + 6) / 5 * (4^3 + 2 + 1)$	44471679	$(9 + 8 + 7^6 * 54/3) * 21$
43769422	$9^8 + 7^6 * (5 + 4 / (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1))$	44473140	$9 * (-8 + (7^6 + 5) * (43 - 2 + 1))$
43803933	$-9 + (8^7 - 6 * 5^4 * 3) * 21$	44473284	$9 * (8 + (7^6 + 5) * (43 - 2 + 1))$
43803951	$9 + (8^7 - 6 * 5^4 * 3) * 21$	44517271	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5) * (4 * 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
43840818	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5) / 4 * 3^{\wedge} (2 + 1)$	44517396	$9^8 + (7^6 + 5) * (4 * 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
43987753	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 * 4) * (3^2 - 1)$	44564310	$(98 + 7 + 65) * (4^3 + 2 - 1)$
43987841	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5 - 4) * (3^2 - 1)$	44564650	$(98 + 7 + 65) * (4^3 + 2 + 1)$
43987903	$9^8 + (7^6 - 5/4) * (3^2 - 1)$	44566645	$9^8 + 76 * (5^4 * 32 - 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
44566797	$9^8+76*(5^4*32+1)$	45752533	$9^8+(7^6-5)*(4^3*2-1)$
44567162	$9^8+(7-6/5)*(4^3^2+1)$	45752763	$9^8+(7^6+5)*(4^3*2-1)$
44581995	$9^8*((7+6)/(5+4)^3*2+1)$	45869001	$9^8+(7^6-54)^*(3+21)$
44619579	$9^8+(7-6+5)*(4^3^2-1)$	45871593	$9^8+(7^6+54)^*(3+21)$
44619591	$9^8+(7-6+5)*(4^3^2+1)$	45927795	$-9+876/5*(4^3^2+1)$
44706629	$9+8*7^6*(5+43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	45927813	$9+876/5*(4^3^2+1)$
44811264	$9^8+(7^6*5-4^{\wedge}3)^*(2+1)$	45987821	$9^8+(7^6-5)*(4^3*2+1)$
44811381	$9^8+(7^6-5)*(4^3+2+1)$	45988071	$9^8+(7^6+5)*(4^3*2+1)$
44811420	$9^8+(7^6*5-4^{\wedge}3)^*(2+1)$	46000708	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4+3)-2-1)$
44811435	$9^8+(7^6*5-4-3)^*(2+1)$	46000742	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4+3)-2+1)$
44811452	$9^8+(7^6*5-4/3)^*(2+1)$	46000776	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4+3)+2-1)$
44811453	$9^8+(7^6*5-4+3)^*(2+1)$	46000810	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4+3)+2+1)$
44811459	$9^8+(7^6*5+4-3)^*(2+1)$	46006281	$9*((87/6+5)*4^3^2+1)$
44811460	$9^8+(7^6*5+4/3)^*(2+1)$	46057554	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1))$
44811477	$9^8+(7^6*5+4+3)^*(2+1)$	46057698	$9*(8+(7^6-5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1))$
44811492	$9^8+(7^6*5+4*3)^*(2+1)$	46061469	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1))$
44811531	$9^8+(7^6+5)*(4^3+2+1)$	46061613	$9*(8+(7^6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1))$
44811648	$9^8+(7^6*5+4^{\wedge}3)^*(2+1)$	46110274	$98*((7^6-5)^4-3*21)$
44818662	$(-98+7^6*(5^4)^3)/21$	46113214	$98*((7^6-5)^4-32-1)$
44826623	$9*(8^7+(6+5)*4^3^2)-1$	46113410	$98*((7^6-5)^4-32+1)$
44826625	$9*(8^7+(6+5)*4^3^2)+1$	46114194	$98*((7^6+5)^4-3*21)$
44998758	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1))$	46115468	$98*((7^6-5)^4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
44998902	$9*(8+(7^6-5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1))$	46115664	$98*((7^6-5)^4-3^{\wedge}2+1)$
45002583	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1))$	46116133	$98*((7^6-5)^4-3)-21$
45002727	$9*(8+(7^6+5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1))$	46116175	$98*((7^6-5)^4-3)+21$
45112438	$98*(7^6*5+4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$	46116399	$98*((7^6-5)^4-3/2+1)$
45143865	$9^8+(7+6-5)*(4^3^2-1)$	46116434	$98*((7^6-5)^4-3/21)$
45143881	$9^8+(7+6-5)*(4^3^2+1)$	46116462	$98*((7^6-5)^4+3/21)$
45163431	$9^8-(7^6-54)^*(3-21)$	46116721	$98*((7^6-5)^4+3)-21$
45164382	$9^8+7^6*54/3-21$	46116763	$98*((7^6-5)^4+3)+21$
45164424	$9^8+7^6*54/3+21$	46116791	$98*((7^6-5)^4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
45165375	$9^8-(7^6+54)^*(3-21)$	46117428	$98*((7^6-5)^4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$
45177203	$-9+8*(7^6*(5+43)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	46118192	$(98*7^6-54)^*(3+2-1)$
45177229	$9+8*(7^6*(5+43)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	46118624	$(98*7^6+54)^*(3+2-1)$
45196310	$9^8+(7+6/5)*(4^3^2+1)$	46119388	$98*((7^6+5)^4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
45281957	$9^8+(7^6-5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$	46120053	$98*((7^6+5)^4-3)-21$
45282147	$9^8+(7^6+5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$	46120095	$98*((7^6+5)^4-3)+21$
45399685	$9^8+(7^6*5-4)^*(3+2-1)$	46120319	$98*((7^6+5)^4-3/2+1)$
45399717	$9^8+(7^6*5+4)^*(3+2-1)$	46120354	$98*((7^6+5)^4-3/21)$
45455943	$(-9+876)/5*(4^3^2+1)$	46120382	$98*((7^6+5)^4+3/21)$
45516972	$9^8+(7^6-54/3)^*21$	46120641	$98*((7^6+5)^4+3)-21$
45517728	$9^8+(7^6+54/3)^*21$	46120683	$98*((7^6+5)^4+3)+21$
45527967	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4*3-21)$	46120711	$98*((7^6+5)^4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
45528111	$9*(8+(7^6-5)^4*3-21)$	46121152	$98*((7^6+5)^4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$
45528129	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4*3-2-1)$	46121348	$98*((7^6+5)^4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$
45528135	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4*3)-21$	46122622	$98*((7^6-5)^4*3*21)$
45528147	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4*3-2+1)$	46123406	$98*((7^6+5)^4+32-1)$
45528165	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4*3+2-1)$	46123602	$98*((7^6+5)^4+32+1)$
45528177	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4*3)+21$	46126542	$98*((7^6+5)^4+3*21)$
45528183	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4*3+2+1)$	46222704	$9^8+(7^6-5^4)^3*(2+1)$
45528279	$9*(8+(7^6-5)^4*3)-21$	46223235	$9^8+(7^6*(5+4)-3)^*(2+1)$
45528309	$9*(8+(7^6-5)^4*3+2-1)$	46223253	$9^8+(7^6*(5+4)+3)^*(2+1)$
45528321	$9*(8+(7^6-5)^4*3)+21$	46223784	$9^8+(7^6+5^4)^3*(2+1)$
45528327	$9*(8+(7^6-5)^4*3+2+1)$	46399311	$(9+876)/5*(4^3^2-1)$
45528345	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4*3+21)$	46399665	$(9+876)/5*(4^3^2+1)$
45528489	$9*(8+(7^6-5)^4*3+21)$	46454515	$9^8-(7+6)^*(5-4^3^2+1)$
45531837	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4*3-21)$	46454541	$9^8-(7+6)^*(5-4^3^2-1)$
45531981	$9*(8+(7^6+5)^4*3-21)$	46454645	$9^8+(7+6)^*(5+4^3^2-1)$
45531999	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4*3-2-1)$	46454671	$9^8+(7+6)^*(5+4^3^2+1)$
45532005	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4*3)-21$	46483644	$(9+8)*7*(-6+5^4*(3/2))-1$
45532017	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4*3-2+1)$	46483678	$(9+8)*7*(-6+5^4*(3/2))+1$
45532035	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4*3+2-1)$	46485072	$(9+8)*7*(6+5^4*(3/2))-1$
45532047	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4*3)+21$	46485106	$(9+8)*7*(6+5^4*(3/2))+1$
45532053	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4*3+2+1)$	46692166	$9^8+(7^6-54)^*(32-1)$
45532149	$9*(8+(7^6+5)^4*3)-21$	46693685	$9^8+(7^6-5)^*(4^3/2-1)$
45532191	$9*(8+(7^6+5)^4*3)+21$	46693995	$9^8+(7^6+5)^*(4^3/2-1)$
45532197	$9*(8+(7^6+5)^4*3+2+1)$	46695514	$9^8+(7^6+54)^*(32-1)$
45532215	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4*3+21)$	46858056	$9/8*7*(65^4/3+21)$
45532359	$9*(8+(7^6+5)^4*3+21)$	46927356	$9^8+(7^6-54)^*(32+1)$
45612882	$(9+(8+7)^*(6+5))*(4^3^2-1)$	46930920	$9^8+(7^6+54)^*(32+1)$
45613230	$(9+(8+7)^*(6+5))*(4^3^2+1)$	47059370	$(9+8*(7^6*5-4))^*(3^2+1)$
45647821	$9+8*7^6*(5+43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	47059527	$9*(-8+7^6/(5^4/3)^{\wedge}-2)-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
47059529	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6/(5^*4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	49412545	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4+3)*21$
47059671	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6/(5^*4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	49412563	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2)-1)$
47059673	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6/(5^*4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	49412579	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2)+1)$
47059830	$(-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4))*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	49412581	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2)-1)$
47257371	$9^*(-8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	49412597	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2)+1)$
47258811	$9^*(-8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	49412615	$98+(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4-3)*21$
47258955	$9^*(8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	49412694	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4-3)*21$
47517362	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)-21$	49412741	$98+(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4+3)*21$
47517404	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)+21$	49412820	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4+3)*21$
47530205	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	49413198	$9+((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4-3)*21$
47645739	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2)-1)$	49413324	$9+((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4+3)*21$
47645757	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2)+1)$	49416574	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/21)$
47645883	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2)-1)$	49752693	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)-21$
47645901	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2)+1)$	49752735	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)+21$
47647448	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*3^{\wedge}2)-1$	49778307	$9^{\wedge}8*(76/54/3^{\wedge}2+1)$
47647450	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*3^{\wedge}2)+1$	49810754	$98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
47647592	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*3^{\wedge}2)-1$	49810950	$98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
47647594	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*3^{\wedge}2)+1$	49968559	$(9+8)*(7/(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
47648096	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*3^{\wedge}2)-1$	49968593	$(9+8)*(7/(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
47648098	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*3^{\wedge}2)+1$	49992495	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$
47648240	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*3^{\wedge}2)-1$	49998700	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^*3^*2+1)$
47648242	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*3^{\wedge}2)+1$	50000154	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$
47649789	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2)-1)$	50000468	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*(3+2)-1)$
47649807	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2)+1)$	50000502	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*(3+2)+1)$
47649951	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2)+1)$	50000727	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(43^*2-1)$
47752649	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	50000923	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(43^*2-1)$
47752713	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	50001148	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*(3+2)-1)$
47765295	$9^{\wedge}8+(7+6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	50001182	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*(3+2)+1)$
47765331	$9^{\wedge}8+(7+6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	50001514	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$
47825130	$(9^{\wedge}8-76*54)*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	50002950	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^*3^*2+1)$
47826290	$(9^{\wedge}8-76*54)*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	50009155	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$
47833090	$(9^{\wedge}8+76*54)*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	50105652	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4-3)*(2+1)$
47834250	$(9^{\wedge}8+76*54)*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	50105670	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4+3)*(2+1)$
47978760	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3+21)$	50223005	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
47998735	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^*3^*2-1)$	50223615	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
47998769	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^*3^*2+1)$	50312816	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
48000765	$(-9+8/7^{\wedge}-6*(5^*4-3))*(2+1)$	50312818	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
48000779	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	50353781	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2+1)$
48000787	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	50458293	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
48000797	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	50458923	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
48000805	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	50689903	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/21)$
48000819	$(9+8/7^{\wedge}-6*(5^*4-3))*(2+1)$	50689921	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/21)$
48002815	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^*3^*2-1)$	50693581	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
48002849	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^*3^*2+1)$	50694231	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
48022824	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(3+21)$	50704547	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432-1)$
48124833	$9^{\wedge}8+(7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	50704563	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432-1)$
48124859	$9^{\wedge}8+(7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	50704565	$9-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432-1)$
48287109	$(9+876/5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	50704581	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432-1)$
48471397	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2-1)$	50708857	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432-1)$
48693852	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)-21$	50708873	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432-1)$
48693894	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)+21$	50708875	$9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432-1)$
48704544	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2+1))$	50708891	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432-1)$
48704688	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2+1))$	50717816	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
48708684	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2+1))$	50717818	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
48708828	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2+1))$	50811555	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
48929131	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	50823584	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
48929211	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	50824251	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)-21)$
48942001	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+32)+1)$	50824269	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)-2-1)$
49020792	$(9+8)*(-7+(6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	50824270	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*54*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
49020826	$(9+8)*(-7+(6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	50824275	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))-21$
49021030	$(9+8)*(7+(6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	50824317	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))+21$
49021064	$(9+8)*(7+(6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	50824405	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
49046799	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)-21$	50824419	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))-21$
49046841	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+21$	50824461	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))+21$
49076010	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	50824466	$98+7^{\wedge}6*54*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
49076056	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	50824467	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)+2+1)$
49382960	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/21)$	50824485	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)+21)$
49411854	$9-((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4+3)*21$	50825152	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
49411980	$9-((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4-3)*21$	50939835	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432+1)$
49412358	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4+3)*21$	50939851	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432+1)$
49412419	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4-3)*21$	50939853	$9-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432+1)$
49412484	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4-3)*21$	50939869	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
50944165	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432+1)$	55050548	$98+7*6*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
50944181	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432+1)$	55059651	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+32))-1$
50944183	$9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432+1)$	55059669	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+32)+1)$
50944199	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432+1)$	55367442	$9^{\wedge}8+(7*6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
50958815	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/21)$	55367536	$9^{\wedge}8+(7*6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
50958833	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/21)$	55487592	$9*((8*76+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
51046853	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	55487610	$9*((8*76+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
51168789	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43*2+1)$	55527977	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-3*21)$
51176628	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43*2+1)$	55530151	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+21)$
51177217	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(43*2+1)$	55530169	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+21)$
51177413	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(43*2+1)$	55530487	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-21)$
51178020	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43*2+1)$	55530505	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-21)$
51185841	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43*2+1)$	55530632	$9-(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-3*21)$
51225482	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	55532697	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-3*21)$
51294973	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2-1)$	55752273	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4*3^{\wedge}2+1$
51710472	$9*((87*6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	55753353	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4*3^{\wedge}2+1$
51710490	$9*((87*6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	56010455	$9*(-8+(7*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)*2)-1$
51765461	$(-9+8/7^{\wedge}6*5*(4*3-2+1))$	56010457	$9*(-8+(7*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)*2)+1$
51765659	$(9+8/7^{\wedge}6*5*(4*3-2+1))$	56010599	$9*(8+(7*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)*2)-1$
51882964	$98*((7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)/2-1)$	56010601	$9*(8+(7*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)*2)+1$
51883160	$98*((7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)/2+1)$	56118492	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3+2)-1)$
51883258	$98*((7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)/2-1)$	56118510	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3+2)+1)$
51883454	$98*((7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)/2+1)$	56469168	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*4*(3+21))$
51904314	$9*(87-65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	56470761	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*4*(3+21)$
51904710	$9*(87-65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	56471337	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*4*(3+21))$
52000841	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3*2))-1$	56471375	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4/3-2)-1$
52000875	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3*2)+1)$	56471377	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4/3-2)+1$
52236139	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2)-1)$	56471422	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*4*(3+21)$
52236155	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2)+1)$	56471475	$(9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4-3))*(2+1)$
52236157	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2)-1)$	56471565	$(9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4+3))*(2-1)$
52236173	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2)+1)$	56471618	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*4*(3+21)$
52746012	$9^{\wedge}8+(7+6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	56471663	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4/3+2)-1$
52746086	$9^{\wedge}8+(7+6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	56471665	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4/3+2)+1$
53177357	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2+1)$	56471721	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*4*(3+21))$
53647931	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	56472297	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*4*(3+21)$
53647939	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	56473872	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*5*4*(3+21))$
53647949	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	56718589	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
53647957	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	56718603	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
54000630	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)-21)$	56811654	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3*21)$
54000774	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)-21)$	56822409	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3))*21$
54000792	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)-2-1)$	56824308	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3))*21$
54000798	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))-21$	56824369	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)*21$
54000810	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)-2+1)$	56824565	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)*21$
54000828	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+2-1)$	56824644	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3))*21$
54000840	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))+21$	56826525	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3))*21$
54000846	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+2+1)$	57026079	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/21))$
54000942	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))-21$	57026223	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/21))$
54000984	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))+21$	57059667	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(54*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
54000990	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+2+1)$	57059863	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(54*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
54001008	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+21)$	57118096	$(9+8)*((7*6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
54001152	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+21)$	57118130	$(9+8)*((7*6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
54253473	$9^{\wedge}(8+7)*((6+5^{\wedge}4*(4*3))^2+1)$	57176775	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54-3*21)$
54263735	$-9*(8+(7-6*5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	57176919	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54-3*21)$
54263737	$-9*(8+(7-6*5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	57177045	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54-32-1)$
54263879	$9*(8-(7-6*5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	57177063	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54-32+1)$
54263881	$9*(8-(7-6*5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	57177126	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54-3-21)$
54693972	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4*(3+2)-1)$	57177180	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54+3-21)$
54735876	$9*((8+76/5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	57177189	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54-32-1)$
55050100	$-98+7*6*(5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	57177207	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54-32+1)$
55050128	$98+7*6*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	57177252	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
55050149	$-98+7*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	57177279	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54)-3*21$
55050161	$9*-8+7*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	57177294	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54-3)-21$
55050175	$9*-8+7*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	57177306	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54-3-2+1)$
55050233	$(9-8)*7*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	57177378	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54+3+2-1)$
55050247	$(9-8)*7*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	57177522	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54+3+2-1)$
55050296	$98+7*6*(5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	57177534	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54+3)+21$
55050305	$9*8+7*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	57177576	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54+3^{\wedge}2+1)$
55050319	$9*8+7*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	57177621	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54+32-1)$
55050331	$98+7*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	57177639	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54+32+1)$
55050345	$98+7*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	57177648	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54-3+21)$
55050352	$-98+7*6*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	57177702	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54+3+21)$
55050380	$98+7*6*(5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	57177765	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54+32-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
57177783	$9^*(8+7^6*54+32+1)$	57649165	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3)-21$
57177909	$9^*(-8+7^6*54+3^*21)$	57649207	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3)+21$
57178053	$9^*(8+7^6*54+3^*21)$	57650019	$98^*(7^6*5+43/2-1)$
57246504	$98^*(7^6*5-(4^3)^2-1)$	57650215	$98^*(7^6*5+43/2+1)$
57246700	$98^*(7^6*5-(4^3)^2+1)$	57650656	$98^*(7^6*5-4+32-1)$
57294965	$-98+7^6*(54^3+2+1)$	57650852	$98^*(7^6*5-4+32+1)$
57295161	$98+7^6*(54^3+2+1)$	57651244	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3+21)$
57328605	$9^*(-8+7^6*(54+3/21))$	57651440	$98^*(7^6*5+4+32-1)$
57328749	$9^*(8+7^6*(54+3/21))$	57651636	$98^*(7^6*5+4+32+1)$
57341662	$98^*((7^6-5^4)^*(3+2)-1)$	57652175	$98^*(7^6*5+43-2^{\wedge}-1)$
57341858	$98^*((7^6-5^4)^*(3+2)+1)$	57652273	$98^*(7^6*5+43+2^{\wedge}-1)$
57394147	$((9^8*7-6^{\wedge}5)^*4+3)/21$	57652714	$98^*(7^6*5+(4+3)^2-1)$
57397109	$((9^8*7+6^{\wedge}5)^*4-3)/21$	57652910	$98^*(7^6*5+(4+3)^2+1)$
57466710	$98^*(7^6*5-43^2-1)$	57653792	$98^*(7^6*5-4+32+1)$
57466906	$98^*(7^6*5-43^2+1)$	57653988	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3-2-1)$
57478666	$98^*(7^6*5-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	57654184	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3-2+1)$
57513726	$9^8*((7/6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)^*2-1)$	57654233	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
57516298	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3*21)$	57654261	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3)-21$
57621452	$98^*((7^6-54)^*(3+2)-1)$	57654303	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3)+21$
57621648	$98^*((7^6-54)^*(3+2)+1)$	57654331	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
57629194	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3*(2+1))$	57654380	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3+2-1)$
57633800	$98^*(7^6*5-(4^*3)^2-1)$	57654576	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3+2+1)$
57633996	$98^*(7^6*5-(4^*3)^2+1)$	57655066	$98^*(7^6*5-4*(3-21))$
57635074	$98^*(7^6*5-4*(32+1))$	57657418	$98^*(7^6*5+4*(3+21))$
57635858	$98^*(7^6*5-4*(32-1))$	57657908	$98^*((7^6+5^4)^*(3+2)+1)$
57637426	$98^*(7^6*5-4^*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	57658594	$98^*(7^6*5+4^*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
57638602	$98^*(7^6*5-4*(3+21))$	57660162	$98^*(7^6*5+4*(32-1))$
57640954	$98^*(7^6*5+4*(3-21))$	57660946	$98^*(7^6*5+4*(32+1))$
57641444	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3-2-1)$	57662024	$98^*(7^6*5+(4^3)^2-1)$
57641640	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3-2+1)$	57662220	$98^*(7^6*5+(4^3)^2+1)$
57641689	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	57666826	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3*(2+1))$
57641717	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3)-21$	57671557	$9+(8^7/(6/5)-4)^*(32+1)$
57641759	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3)+21$	57671803	$-9+(8^7/(6/5)+4)^*(32+1)$
57641787	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	57671821	$9+(8^7/(6/5)+4)^*(32+1)$
57641836	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3+2-1)$	57674372	$98^*((7^6+54)^*(3+2)-1)$
57642032	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3+2+1)$	57674568	$98^*((7^6+54)^*(3+2)+1)$
57642228	$98^*(7^6*5+4-3^*21)$	57779722	$98^*(7^6*5+4^3*21)$
57643110	$98^*(7^6*5-(4+3)^2-1)$	57808971	$9^8*((7-6/5-4)^{\wedge}-3^*2+1)$
57643306	$98^*(7^6*5-(4+3)^2+1)$	57817354	$98^*(7^6*5+(4^3)^2+1)$
57643747	$98^*(7^6*5-43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	57829114	$98^*(7^6*5+43^2-1)$
57643845	$98^*(7^6*5-43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	57829310	$98^*(7^6*5+43^2+1)$
57644384	$98^*(7^6*5-4-32-1)$	57934912	$(9+8)^*((7+6)^*(5+4^3^2)-1)$
57644580	$98^*(7^6*5-4-32+1)$	57934946	$(9+8)^*((7+6)^*(5+4^3^2)+1)$
57644776	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3-21)$	57954162	$98^*((7^6+5^4)^*(3+2)-1)$
57645168	$98^*(7^6*5+4-32-1)$	57954358	$98^*((7^6+5^4)^*(3+2)+1)$
57645364	$98^*(7^6*5+4-32+1)$	58000940	$(9+8)^*(7^6*5+4^3*2)-1)$
57645805	$98^*(7^6*5-43/2-1)$	58000974	$(9+8)^*(7^6*5+4^3*2)+1)$
57646001	$98^*(7^6*5-43/2+1)$	58118615	$9-8*7^6*(5/4-3^*21)$
57646148	$98^*(7^6*5-4*(3+2)+1)$	58236174	$9^*(-8+7^6*(54+3-2)-1)$
57646813	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3)-21$	58236192	$9^*(-8+7^6*(54+3-2)+1)$
57646855	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3)+21$	58236336	$9^*(8+7^6*(54+3-2)+1)$
57646883	$98^*(7^6*5-4^3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	58929228	$9^8+(7^6*5-4)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
57647303	$98^*(7^6*5-4-3)-21$	58929444	$9^8+(7^6*5+4)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
57647345	$98^*(7^6*5-4-3)+21$	58939731	$(9+8)^*((7+6-5^4*3)^2-1)$
57647555	$98^*(7^6*5-4)^*3^*21$	58939765	$(9+8)^*((7+6-5^4*3)^2+1)$
57647604	$98^*(7^6*5-4-3/21)$	59255712	$-9+(8/7^{\wedge}-6-5^4)^*3^*21$
57647632	$98^*(7^6*5-4+3/21)$	59255730	$9+(8/7^{\wedge}-6-5^4)^*3^*21$
57647681	$98^*(7^6*5-4)+3^*21$	59267871	$-9+8*(7^6-54)^*3^*21$
57647891	$98^*(7^6*5-4+3)-21$	59267889	$9+8*(7^6-54)^*3^*21$
57647898	$98^*(7^6*5-4/(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	59290569	$9+8*(7^6-5-4)^*3^*21$
57647933	$98^*(7^6*5-4+3)+21$	59291505	$(-9+(8^*7^6-54)^*3)^*21$
57647938	$98^*(7^6*5+4*(3-21))$	59292333	$9+(8^*(7^6-5)-4)^*3^*21$
57648087	$98^*(7^6*5+4-3)-21$	59292387	$9^*(8^*(7^6-5)^*(4+3)-21)$
57648122	$98^*(7^6*5+4/(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	59292765	$9^*(8^*(7^6-5)^*(4+3)+21)$
57648129	$98^*(7^6*5+4-3)+21$	59292837	$9+(8^*(7^6-5)+4)^*3^*21$
57648339	$98^*(7^6*5+4)-3^*21$	59294088	$9^8*((7^6-5)^*(4+3)+21)$
57648388	$98^*(7^6*5+4-3/21)$	59294475	$9+8*(7^6-5/4)^*3^*21$
57648416	$98^*(7^6*5+4+3/21)$	59294601	$9+8*(7^6-5+4)^*3^*21$
57648465	$98^*(7^6*5+4)+3^*21$	59295609	$9+8*(7^6+5-4)^*3^*21$
57648675	$98^*(7^6*5+4+3)-21$	59296104	$9^8*((7^6+5)^*(4+3)-21)$
57648717	$98^*(7^6*5+4+3)+21$	59297373	$9+(8^*(7^6+5)-4)^*3^*21$
57648745	$98^*(7^6*5+4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	59297427	$9^*(8^*(7^6+5)^*(4+3)-21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
59297805	$9*(8*(7^6+5)*(4+3)+21)$	61603511	$(9-8*7)*(6-5*4^3+2+1)$
59297877	$9+(8*(7^6+5)+4)*3*21$	61603605	$(9-8*7)*(6-5*4^3+2-1)$
59298309	$(-9+(8*7^6+54)*3)*21$	61603793	$(9-8*7)*(6-5*(4^3+2+1))$
59298687	$(9+(8*7^6+54)*3)*21$	61603887	$(-9+8*7)*(6+5*(4^3+2-1))$
59299641	$9+8*(7^6+5+4)*3*21$	61604075	$(-9+8*7)*(6+5*4^3+2-1)$
59322303	$-9+8*(7^6+54)*3*21$	61604169	$(-9+8*7)*(6+5*4^3+2+1)$
59322321	$9+8*(7^6+54)*3*21$	61604357	$(-9+8*7)*(6+5*(4^3+2+1))$
59334462	$-9+(8*7^6+5^4)*3*21$	61725816	$-9*(8-7*6^4(5+4-3)*21)$
59334480	$9+(8*7^6+5^4)*3*21$	61972565	$(9+8)*(7^6-54)*(32-1)$
59383601	$(9+8)*(-7+(6-5^4*3)^2-1)$	62001006	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5-4^3+2)+1)$
59383635	$(9+8)*(-7+(6-5^4*3)^2+1)$	62001040	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5-4^3+2)-1)$
59383839	$(9+8)*(7+(6-5^4*3)^2-1)$	62029481	$(9+8)*(7^6+54)*(32-1)$
59383873	$(9+8)*(7+(6-5^4*3)^2+1)$	62076728	$98*((7+6)^4+4^3+2-1)$
59610087	$-9+8*(7^6+5^4)*3*21$	62076924	$98*((7+6)^4+5+4^3+2+1)$
59610105	$9+8*(7^6+5^4)*3*21$	62177492	$(9^8-765)*(4/3+2+1)$
59698464	$9*8*7^6*(5+43/21)$	62179702	$(9^8+765)*(4/3+2+1)$
59701875	$(9+8)*((7-6-5^4*3)^2-1)$	62468892	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*(4-3*21))$
59701909	$(9+8)*((7-6-5^4*3)^2+1)$	62469036	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*(4-3*21))$
59829375	$(9+8)*((7-6+5^4*3)^2-1)$	62471358	$-9*(8+7^6*(5-4^3)+21)$
59829409	$(9+8)*((7-6+5^4*3)^2+1)$	62471502	$9*(8-7^6*(5-4^3)-21)$
59869813	$9^8+(7^6-5)*((4^3)^2-1)$	62471528	$-9*(8+7^6*(5-4^3)+2)-1$
59871243	$9^8+(7^6+5)*((4^3)^2-1)$	62471530	$-9*(8+7^6*(5-4^3)+2)+1$
60000565	$(9+8)*((7^6*5-4)*3*2-1)$	62471564	$-9*(8+7^6*(5-4^3)-2)-1$
60000599	$(9+8)*((7^6*5-4)*3*2+1)$	62471566	$-9*(8+7^6*(5-4^3)-2)+1$
60000973	$(9+8)*(7^6*5^4*3/2-1)$	62471672	$9*(8-7^6*(5-4^3)-2)-1$
60001007	$(9+8)*(7^6*5^4*3/2+1)$	62471674	$9*(8-7^6*(5-4^3)-2)+1$
60001381	$(9+8)*((7^6*5+4)*3*2-1)$	62471708	$9*(8-7^6*(5-4^3)+2)-1$
60001415	$(9+8)*((7^6*5+4)*3*2+1)$	62471710	$9*(8-7^6*(5-4^3)+2)+1$
60086016	$9^8+(7+6)*5*(4^3+2-1)$	62471736	$-9*(8+7^6*(5-4^3)-21)$
60086068	$9^8+(7+6)*(5^4+3^2-1)$	62471880	$9*(8-7^6*(5-4^3)+21)$
60086094	$9^8+(7+6)*(5^4+3^2+1)$	62473096	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4*3)^2-1)$
60086146	$9^8+(7+6)*5*(4^3+2+1)$	62473130	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4*3)^2+1)$
60105101	$9^8+(7^6-5)*((4^3)^2+1)$	62474202	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*(4-3*21))$
60106551	$9^8+(7^6+5)*((4^3)^2+1)$	62474346	$9*(8-(7^6+5)*(4-3*21))$
60111882	$-9^8(-8+7+6)*(5-4^3+2)+1$	62510058	$(9^8-7^6*543)*(-2-1)$
60148601	$(9+8)*(-7+(6+5^4*3)^2-1)$	62911671	$9*(8^7/(6/5)^4-321)$
60148635	$(9+8)*(-7+(6+5^4*3)^2+1)$	62917449	$9*(8^7/(6/5)^4+321)$
60148839	$(9+8)*(7+(6+5^4*3)^2-1)$	63231802	$9^8+7*((6+5)^4+3^2-1)$
60148873	$(9+8)*(7+(6+5^4*3)^2+1)$	63231816	$9^8+7*((6+5)^4+3^2+1)$
60229980	$-9^8(-8+7+6)*(5-4^3+2)-1$	63410214	$98*((7^6-5)^4+3/2+1)$
60233551	$-9+8*((7^6-5)^4+3-21)$	63468889	$9^8(-8+7)*(65^4+32+1)$
60233569	$9+8*((7^6-5)^4+3-21)$	63529353	$(9+(8-7^6*5)^4)*3^2(2+1)$
60233887	$-9+8*((7^6-5)^4+3+21)$	63529480	$(-98+7^6*54)^3(2+1)$
60233905	$9+8*((7^6-5)^4+3+21)$	63529577	$9*((-8+7^6*5)^4+3^2-2)-1$
60238671	$-9+8*((7^6+5)^4+3-21)$	63529579	$9*((-8+7^6*5)^4+3^2+2)+1$
60238689	$9+8*((7^6+5)^4+3-21)$	63529613	$9*((-8+7^6*5)^4+3^2+2)-1$
60239007	$-9+8*((7^6+5)^4+3+21)$	63529615	$9*((-8+7^6*5)^4+3^2+2)+1$
60239025	$9+8*((7^6+5)^4+3+21)$	63529839	$(9-(8-7^6*5)^4)*3^2(2+1)$
60353676	$9*(-8+7^6*(54+3)-21)$	63530225	$9*((-8+7^6*5^4)*3^2-2)-1$
60353820	$9*(8+7^6*(54+3)-21)$	63530227	$9*((-8+7^6*5^4)*3^2+2)+1$
60353838	$9*(-8+7^6*(54+3)-2-1)$	63530261	$9*((-8+7^6*5^4)*3^2+2)-1$
60353844	$9*(-8+7^6*(54+3))-21$	63530263	$9*((-8+7^6*5^4)*3^2+2)+1$
60353886	$9*(-8+7^6*(54+3))+21$	63530369	$9*(-8+7^6*5^4*3^2-2)-1$
60353892	$9*(-8+7^6*(54+3))+2+1$	63530371	$9*(-8+7^6*5^4*3^2+2)+1$
60353988	$9*(8+7^6*(54+3))-21$	63530549	$9+(8+7^6*54)^3(2+1)$
60354030	$9*(8+7^6*(54+3))+21$	63530551	$9*(8+7^6*5^4*3^2+2)+1$
60354036	$9*(8+7^6*(54+3)+2+1)$	63530657	$9*((8+7^6*5^4)*3^2-2)-1$
60354054	$9*(-8+7^6*(54+3)+21)$	63530659	$9*((8+7^6*5^4)*3^2+2)+1$
60354198	$9*(8+7^6*(54+3)+21)$	63530693	$9*((8+7^6*5^4)*3^2+2)-1$
60458773	$9^8+7^6*(5+(4^3)^2-1)$	63530695	$9*((8+7^6*5^4)*3^2+2)+1$
60471595	$9+8*7^6*(5/4+3*21)$	63531081	$(-9+(8+7^6*5^4)*3^2(2+1))$
60521664	$98*((7^6-5)/4-3)*21$	63531305	$9*((8+7^6*5^4)*4^3-2)-1$
60526809	$98*((7^6+5)/4-3)*21$	63531307	$9*((8+7^6*5^4)*4^3-2)+1$
60534012	$98*((7^6-5)/4+3)*21$	63531341	$9*((8+7^6*5^4)*4^3+2)-1$
60539157	$98*((7^6+5)/4+3)*21$	63531343	$9*((8+7^6*5^4)*4^3+2)+1$
60597231	$(9+8)*((7+6+5^4*3)^2-1)$	63531440	$(98+7^6*54)^3(2+1)$
60597265	$(9+8)*((7+6+5^4*3)^2+1)$	63531567	$(9+(8+7^6*5^4)*3^2(2+1))$
60694071	$9^8+7^6*(5+(4^3)^2+1)$	63699534	$9^8((8+7)/6)^4(-5+4^3+2-1)$
61174555	$(9-8*7^6/5)*(-4-321)$	63702450	$9^8((8+7)/6)^4(5+4^3+2+1)$
61180405	$(9+8*7^6/5)*(4+321)$	63765686	$-9*8+7^6*(543-2+1)$
61282316	$9^8+7^6*5*(4^3/2-1)$	63765830	$9*8+7^6*(543-2+1)$
61603323	$(9-8*7)*(6-5*(4^3+2-1))$	63870594	$9^8-7^6*(5-4^3)*(2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
63971663	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*32-1)$	68848065	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5)*(4+321)$
63971697	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*32+1)$	68874625	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)/5^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}2-1$
63998319	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	68874627	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)/5^{\wedge}4-3)^{\wedge}2+1$
63998353	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3/2+1)$	68874637	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)/5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
64000984	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2-1)$	68874639	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)/5^{\wedge}4+3)^{\wedge}2+1$
64001128	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2-1)$	69145762	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$
64003759	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	69145958	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
64003793	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3/2+1)$	69175304	$9*8/7*((6^{\wedge}5+4)/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
64030415	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge}32-1)$	69175554	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4-3)-21)$
64030449	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge}32+1)$	69176779	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5/4)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$
64070538	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	69176975	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5/4)^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
64236282	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2+1)$	69177661	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4-3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$
64236426	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2+1)$	69177906	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4-3)+2+1)$
64540557	$9^{\wedge}8*((7-6-(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)/2+1)$	69178249	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5/4)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$
64576488	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(54^{\wedge}3+21)$	69178445	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5/4)^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
64599606	$9^{\wedge}8*((7-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)/2+1)$	69179670	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4-3)+21)$
64942071	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-21)$	69209266	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$
64942089	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-21)$	69209462	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
64942221	$(-9+8/7^{\wedge}-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	69545014	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$
64942275	$(9+8/7^{\wedge}-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	69545210	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
64942407	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+21)$	69648110	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32-1)$
64942425	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+21)$	69648306	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32-1)$
65047084	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3*(2+1))$	69883408	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32+1)$
65674288	$(9/(8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2)))^{\wedge}-1$	69883604	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32+1)$
65970795	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge}(32+1)$	70001104	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2-1)$
66031383	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge}(32+1)$	70001206	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2+1)$
66118640	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}21)$	70589265	$(-9+8/7^{\wedge}-6*5^{\wedge})^{\wedge}(4*3+2+1)$
66118836	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}21)$	70589535	$(9+8/7^{\wedge}-6*5^{\wedge})^{\wedge}(4*3+2+1)$
66223574	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3*(2+1))$	70777827	$-9*(87-6*5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
66624649	$(9+8)*7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	70778043	$-9*(87-6*5^{\wedge}(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
66624887	$(9+8)*7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	70778088	$-9*(87-6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
66674853	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70778151	$-9*(87-6*5^{\wedge}(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
66676293	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70778375	$-9*(8*7-6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
66676437	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70778377	$-9*(8*7-6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
66677877	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70778744	$-9*(8+7-6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
66701808	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70778746	$-9*(8+7-6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
66704925	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70778870	$-9*(8-7-6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
66706824	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70778872	$-9*(8-7-6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
66706885	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}21$	70778888	$9*(8-7+6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
66707081	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}21$	70778890	$9*(8-7+6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
66707160	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70779014	$9*(8+7+6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
66707496	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70779016	$9*(8+7+6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
66709041	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70779383	$9*(8*7+6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
66712014	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70779385	$9*(8*7+6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
66736089	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70779609	$9*(87+6*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
66737529	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70779672	$9*(87+6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
66737673	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	70779933	$9*(87+6*5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
66739113	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	71282481	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
66929208	$(9/(-8+7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$	71530593	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)^{\wedge}2+1)$
67061286	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	71548431	$((9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}5-4)/3-21$
67061430	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$	71548473	$((9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}5-4)/3+21$
67400064	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	71743260	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)^{\wedge}(4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
67498841	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	71744491	$((9^{\wedge}8-7-6)^{\wedge}5-4)/3-21$
67498855	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	71744517	$((9^{\wedge}8+7-6)^{\wedge}5+4)/3-21$
67762683	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3-21)$	71745810	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)^{\wedge}(4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
67762827	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3-21)$	71753077	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
67763061	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3+21)$	71868834	$9/8*(7^{\wedge}6*543+2-1)$
67763205	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3+21)$	71940597	$((9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}5+4)/3-21$
67768443	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3-21)$	71940639	$((9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6)^{\wedge}5+4)/3+21$
67768587	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3-21)$	71988375	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}(4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
67768821	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3+21)$	71998111	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
67768965	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3+21)$	71998145	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
67813841	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	72004265	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
67813855	$9^{\wedge}8+7*((6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	72011877	$(9^{\wedge}8-76^{\wedge}5/4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}21$
68001105	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	72133542	$9/8*(7^{\wedge}6*(543+2)-1)$
68001139	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	72354037	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
68112000	$9*((876+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	72354063	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
68112008	$9*(876+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$	72354207	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
68112009	$9*(876+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2/1$	72354233	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
68112010	$9*(876+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$	72394074	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^{\wedge}((5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
68112018	$9*((876+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	72471793	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)^{\wedge}21$
68801265	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6/5)^{\wedge}(4+321)$	72589335	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
72589361	$-9*8+7^6*(5^4-3^2+1)$	75536757	$(9+8*(7^6+5)/4)*321$
72589505	$9*8+7^6*(5^4-3^2+1)$	75883311	$(-98+7^6*5^4*3)*(2+1)$
72589531	$98+7^6*(5^4-3^2+1)$	75883507	$-98+7^6*5^4*3*(2+1)$
72706984	$-98+7^6*(5^4-3^2-1)$	75883533	$9*(-8+7^6*5^4*3/(2+1))$
72707010	$-9*8+7^6*(5^4-3^2-1)$	75883590	$9-(8-7^6*5^4*3)*(2+1)$
72707154	$9*8+7^6*(5^4-3^2-1)$	75883638	$9+(8+7^6*5^4*3)*(2+1)$
72707180	$98+7^6*(5^4-3^2-1)$	75883703	$98+7^6*5^4*3*(2+1)$
72817778	$(9/(8^7/6*5^4*3+2))^{\wedge-1}$	75883899	$(98+7^6*5^4*3)*(2+1)$
72939342	$(-98+7^6*5^4)*(32-1)$	76000897	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5-43)+21)$
72941397	$9-(8-7^6*5^4)*4*(32-1)$	76001611	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5-43)-21)$
72942141	$9-(8-7^6*5^4)*(32-1)$	76201551	$9*(8*(7^6-54)^3*2-1)$
72942637	$9+(8+7^6*5^4)*(32-1)$	76201569	$9*(8*(7^6-54)^3*2+1)$
72943381	$9+(8+7^6*5^4)*4*(32-1)$	76213440	$9*8*(7^6*(5+4)-321)$
72945418	$(98+7^6*5^4)*(32-1)$	76232169	$9*((8*7^6+54)^3*2-1)$
73059768	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4^3)-21)$	76232187	$9*((8*7^6-54)^3*2+1)$
73059912	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4^3)-21)$	76234239	$9*(8*(7^6*(5+4)-32)-1)$
73059938	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4^3)-2)-1$	76234257	$9*(8*(7^6*(5+4)-32)+1)$
73059940	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4^3)-2)+1$	76236119	$9*8*(7^6*(5+4)-3^2)-1$
73059974	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4^3)+2)-1$	76236121	$9*8*(7^6*(5+4)-3^2)+1$
73059976	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4^3)+2)+1$	76236983	$9*8*(7^6*(5+4)+3^2)-1$
73060082	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4^3)-2)-1$	76236985	$9*8*(7^6*(5+4)+3^2)+1$
73060084	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4^3)-2)+1$	76238847	$9*(8*(7^6*(5+4)+32)-1)$
73060118	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4^3)+2)-1$	76238865	$9*(8*(7^6*(5+4)+32)+1)$
73060120	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4^3)+2)+1$	76240917	$9*((8*7^6+54)^3*2-1)$
73060146	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4^3)+21)$	76240935	$9*((8*7^6+54)^3*2+1)$
73060290	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4^3)+21)$	76259664	$9*8*(7^6*(5+4)+321)$
73177559	$-98+7^6*(5^4-3)-21$	76271535	$9*(8*(7^6+54)^3*2-1)$
73177601	$-98+7^6*(5^4-3)+21$	76271553	$9*(8*(7^6+54)^3*2+1)$
73177755	$98+7^6*(5^4-3)-21$	77177646	$-98+7^6*(5^4+32-1)$
73177797	$98+7^6*(5^4-3)+21$	77177842	$98+7^6*(5^4+32-1)$
73295255	$-9*8+7^6*(5^4-3+2-1)$	77412944	$-98+7^6*(5^4+32+1)$
73295399	$9*8+7^6*(5^4-3+2-1)$	77413140	$98+7^6*(5^4+32+1)$
73397907	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*(5^4-3)^2-1$	77645106	$(-98+7^6*5^4)*(32+1)$
73516005	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*((5^4-3)^2+1)$	77647293	$9-(8-7^6*5^4)*4*(32+1)$
73547334	$-98+7^6*(5^4+3/21)$	77648085	$9-(8-7^6*5^4)*(32+1)$
73547530	$98+7^6*(5^4+3/21)$	77648242	$-98+7^6*5^4*(32+1)$
73765851	$-9*8+7^6*(5^4+3-2+1)$	77648438	$98+7^6*5^4*(32+1)$
73765995	$9*8+7^6*(5^4+3-2+1)$	77648613	$9+(8+7^6*5^4)*(32+1)$
73883453	$-98+7^6*(5^4+3)-21$	77649405	$9+(8+7^6*5^4)*4*(32+1)$
73883495	$-98+7^6*(5^4+3)+21$	77651574	$(98+7^6*5^4)*(32+1)$
73883649	$98+7^6*(5^4+3)-21$	78774263	$-9+8^7*(65/(4/3)^2+1)$
73883691	$98+7^6*(5^4+3)+21$	78774281	$9+8^7*(65/(4/3)^2+1)$
73923151	$(9-8^7)*(6*(5-4^3^2)+1)$	78812017	$9^8+7^6*(5^4-321)$
73923245	$(9-8^7)*(6*(5-4^3^2)-1)$	78917586	$(9^8-765)*(4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
73925971	$(-9+8^7)*(6*(5+4^3^2)-1)$	78920391	$(9^8+765)*(4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
73926065	$(-9+8^7)*(6*(5+4^3^2)+1)$	78929666	$9^8+7^6*5*(4^3-2-1)$
74001149	$-9*8+7^6*(5^4+3+2-1)$	79056714	$9+(8*(7^6-5)^4-3)^2*21$
74001293	$9*8+7^6*(5^4+3+2-1)$	79056840	$9+(8*(7^6-5)^4+3)^2*21$
74106495	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*((5^4+3)^2-1)$	79063434	$9+(8*(7^6+5)^4-3)^2*21$
74224593	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*((5^4+3)^2+1)$	79063560	$9+(8*(7^6+5)^4+3)^2*21$
74354070	$-98+7^6*(5^4+3^2+1)$	79400262	$9^8+7^6*(5*(4^3-2)-1)$
74354096	$-9*8+7^6*(5^4+3^2+1)$	79870858	$9^8+7^6*((5^4+3)/2-1)$
74354240	$9*8+7^6*(5^4+3^2+1)$	79953615	$(9+8*(7+6^5))*(4^3^2-1)$
74354266	$98+7^6*(5^4+3^2+1)$	79954225	$(9+8*(7+6^5))*(4^3^2+1)$
74471719	$-98+7^6*(5^4+3^2-1)$	79997929	$9+8*(7^6-5)*(4^3+21)$
74471745	$-9*8+7^6*(5^4+3^2-1)$	80001201	$(9+8)*((7^6*5^4-3)^2-1)$
74471889	$9*8+7^6*(5^4+3^2-1)$	80001235	$(9+8)*((7^6*5^4-3)^2+1)$
74471915	$98+7^6*(5^4+3^2-1)$	80001405	$(9+8)*((7^6*5^4+3)^2-1)$
74579959	$-9+8^7*(65/(4/3)^2-1)$	80001439	$(9+8)*((7^6*5^4+3)^2+1)$
74579977	$9+8^7*(65/(4/3)^2-1)$	80001754	$9+(8*7^6+5)*(4^3+21)$
74707017	$-98+7^6*5*(4^3-2-1)$	80004729	$9+8*(7^6+5)*(4^3+21)$
74707043	$-9*8+7^6*(5^4+3^2+1)$	80106156	$9^8+7^6*5*(4^3-2+1)$
74707213	$98+7^6*5*(4^3-2-1)$	80327655	$9*(-8-7+(65^4-3)/2-1)$
75177809	$98+7^6*(5^4*3^2-1)$	80327673	$9*(-8-7+(65^4-3)/2+1)$
75412911	$-98+7^6*(5^4*3^2+1)$	80327682	$9*(-8-7+(65^4+3)/2-1)$
75412937	$-9*8+7^6*(5/4^{\wedge}-3^2+1)$	80327700	$9*(-8-7+(65^4+3)/2+1)$
75413107	$98+7^6*(5^4*3^2+1)$	80327925	$9*(8+7+(65^4-3)/2-1)$
75524559	$(-9+8*(7^6-5)/4)^3*321$	80327943	$9*(8+7+(65^4-3)/2+1)$
75527439	$-9+8*(7^6-5)/4^3*321$	80327952	$9*(8+7+(65^4+3)/2-1)$
75527457	$9+8*(7^6-5)/4^3*321$	80327970	$9*(8+7+(65^4+3)/2+1)$
75533859	$-9+8*(7^6+5)/4^3*321$	80341454	$9^8+7^6*(5^4*3^2-1)$
75533877	$9+8*(7^6+5)/4^3*321$	80471835	$-9*(8+7^6*(5-43)^2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
80471853	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)^*2-1)$	85766004	$9*((-8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*3/2-1)$
80472051	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))^*2-1)$	85766166	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*54^*3)/2+1)$
80472069	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))^*2+1)$	85766238	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*3/2+1)$
80576752	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	85975425	$9^{\wedge}8*((7-6-(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
80701726	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)-21)$	85997407	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43-21)$
80703735	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	85998121	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43+21)$
80703833	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	86004717	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43-21)$
80703882	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)+2-1)$	86005431	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43+21)$
80705842	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)+21)$	86211621	$9^{\wedge}8*((7-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
80708586	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3)-21)$	86328108	$(9+8)*((7+6)^*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
80710693	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	86328142	$(9+8)*((7+6)^*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
80710938	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3)+2+1)$	86469957	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3))^*21$
80712702	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3)+21)$	86470848	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4+3)^*21$
80805630	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^*4)^*321$	86471856	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3))^*21$
80818470	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^*4)^*321$	86471917	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4/3)^*2-1)$
80942414	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^*21)$	86472113	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4/3)^*2+1)$
80942610	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^*21)$	86472192	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3))^*21$
81530685	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)^*21)$	86473200	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3))^*21$
81753242	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$	86474073	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3))^*21$
81880233	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43^*2+1)$	86669496	$-9*8*(7-6/5^{\wedge}-4^*321)$
81887193	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(43^*2+1)$	86670504	$9*8*(7+6/5^{\wedge}-4^*321)$
81988540	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	87293879	$9*(-8+(7^*6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
82001336	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^*3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	87293881	$9*(-8+(7^*6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
82001370	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^*3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	87294023	$9*(8+(7^*6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
82574909	$-9*(8+7*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))-1$	87294025	$9*(8+(7^*6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
82574911	$-9*(8+7*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))+1$	88938225	$9*(-8+((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3)^*21)$
82575053	$9*(8-7*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))-1$	88939359	$9*(-8+((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3)^*21)$
82575055	$9*(8-7*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))+1$	88945785	$9*(-8+((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3)^*21)$
82575665	$-9*(8-7*(6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))-1$	88946919	$9*(-8+((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3)^*21)$
82575667	$-9*(8-7*(6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))+1$	89128629	$9-(8-76)^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
82575809	$9*(8+7*(6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))-1$	89128883	$-9-(8-76)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
82575811	$9*(8+7*(6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))+1$	89128901	$9-(8-76)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
82589526	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3+21))$	89129037	$9-(8-76)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
82589670	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3+21))$	89129291	$-9-(8-76)^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
82727649	$9^{\wedge}8*(7/6^{\wedge}5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	89129309	$9-(8-76)^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
83338024	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	89413069	$(-9+8/7^{\wedge}-6*5)^*(4*(3+2)-1)$
83338220	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	89413411	$(9+8/7^{\wedge}-6*5)^*(4*(3+2)-1)$
84118937	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	89997588	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43^*2-1))$
84119107	$9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	89997732	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43^*2-1))$
84119133	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	90000856	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
84129331	$(9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	90000890	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
84381021	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6/5/4-3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	90001413	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3+21))$
84589559	$-9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5/(4^*3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$	90001468	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3+2)-1)$
84589703	$9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	90001502	$(9+8)*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3+2)+1$
84589729	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	90001557	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3+21))$
84706649	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)-3)^*2-1$	90002080	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
84706651	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)-3)^*2+1$	90002114	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
84706713	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^*(3-21)$	90005238	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(43^*2-1))$
84706757	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)+3)^*2-1$	90005382	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(43^*2-1))$
84706759	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)+3)^*2+1$	90350601	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4*(3+21)$
84707217	$9-(8^*7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^*(3-21)$	90354921	$9+(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4*(3+21)$
84707801	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)-3)^*2-1$	90358281	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4*(3+21)$
84707803	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)-3)^*2+1$	90437610	$(-9-8^*7^*6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
84707865	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^*(3-21)$	90438300	$(-9-8^*7^*6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
84707909	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)+3)^*2-1$	90441060	$(9+8^*7^*6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
84707911	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)+3)^*2+1$	90441750	$(9+8^*7^*6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
84824831	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	90687529	$(9/(8+(7+6)^{\wedge}(5+4+3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
84824857	$-9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5/(4^*3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	91056375	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43^*2-1)$
84825001	$9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5/(4^*3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	91056393	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43^*2+1)$
84825027	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	91056591	$9*((8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43)^*2-1)$
84945267	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^*321$	91056609	$9*((8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43)^*2+1)$
84968307	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^*321$	91060245	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3+21)-1)$
84968451	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^*321$	91060263	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3+21)+1)$
84991491	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^*321$	91060389	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3+21)-1)$
85295427	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	91060407	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3+21)+1)$
85295597	$9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	91064115	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43^*2-1)$
85295623	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	91064133	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43^*2+1)$
85305965	$(9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	91064331	$9*((8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43)^*2-1)$
85719126	$(9-8^*7^*6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	91064349	$9*((8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43)^*2+1)$
85719780	$(9-8^*7^*6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	91796828	$(-9+8^*7)^*((6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
85722396	$(-9+8^*7^*6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	91796922	$(-9+8^*7)^*((6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
85723050	$(-9+8^*7^*6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	92001535	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3)^*2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
92115180	$9^*(-8+(7^6-5)*(43^2+1))$	98825187	$(9+8/7^{\wedge}6-6*5*(4+3))*(2+1)$
92115324	$9^*(8+(7^6-5)*(43^2+1))$	98825197	$9+(8*7^6*5+4/3)*21$
92119095	$9^*(-8+7^6*(54+32+1))$	98825337	$9+8*(7^6*5+4-3)*21$
92119239	$9^*(8+7^6*(54+32+1))$	98825393	$9+8*(7^6*5+4/3)*21$
92123010	$9^*(-8+(7^6+5)*(43^2+1))$	98825778	$9+(8*(7^6*5+4)-3)*21$
92123154	$9^*(8+(7^6+5)*(43^2+1))$	98825904	$9+(8*(7^6*5+4)+3)*21$
92157111	$9^*((8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}4-321)$	98826345	$9+8*(7^6*5+4+3)*21$
92159433	$9^*((8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}4-3*21)$	98832195	$(-9+8*(7^6*5+43))*21$
92159679	$9^*(8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}4-321$	98832573	$(9+8*(7^6*5+43))*21$
92160321	$9^*(8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}4+321$	98835903	$-9+8*(7^6*5+4^3)*21$
92160567	$9^*((8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}4+3*21)$	98835921	$9+8*(7^6*5+4^3)*21$
92162889	$9^*((8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}4+321)$	99088469	$-9*(8+7*6*(5-4^3^{\wedge}2))-1$
92232798	$98^*((7^6-5)/4*32-1)$	99088471	$-9*(8+7*6*(5-4^3^{\wedge}2))+1$
92232994	$98^*((7^6-5)/4*32+1)$	99088613	$9*(8-7*6*(5-4^3^{\wedge}2))-1$
92240638	$98^*((7^6+5)/4*32-1)$	99088615	$9*(8-7*6*(5-4^3^{\wedge}2))+1$
92240834	$98^*((7^6+5)/4*32+1)$	99092249	$-9*(8-7*6*(5+4^3^{\wedge}2))-1$
93238371	$(9^{\wedge}8-76*54^3)*(2+1)$	99092251	$-9*(8-7*6*(5+4^3^{\wedge}2))+1$
93297420	$9^{\wedge}8*(7/6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3/2+1)$	99092393	$9*(8+7*6*(5+4^3^{\wedge}2))-1$
93585051	$(-98+7*65)*(4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$	99092395	$9*(8+7*6*(5+4^3^{\wedge}2))+1$
93585765	$(-98+7*65)*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$	100001633	$(9+8)*(7^6*5*(4+3^2)-1)$
93882390	$(9*8+7^6*(5-43))*-21$	100001667	$(9+8)*(7^6*5*(4+3^2)+1)$
93883545	$(9+8+7^6*(5-43))*-21$	100236957	$9+8*7^6*(5*43/2-1)$
93883725	$-9-(8+7^6*(5-43))*21$	100617108	$(-9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6)*(5+4-(3*2)^{\wedge}2-1)$
93883743	$9-(8+7^6*(5-43))*21$	100617267	$(9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6)*(5+4-(3*2)^{\wedge}2-1)$
93883830	$9*-8-7^6*(5-43)*21$	100710000	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*321)$
93883881	$(9-8+7^6*(5-43))*-21$	101178139	$-9+8*(7^6*5*43/2+1)$
93883885	$-9-8-7^6*(5-43)*21$	101178141	$9+8*(7^6*5*43/2-1)$
93883901	$-9+8-7^6*(5-43)*21$	101178157	$9+8*(7^6*5*43/2+1)$
93883903	$9-8-7^6*(5-43)*21$	101204900	$9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6-5*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$
93883919	$9+8-7^6*(5-43)*21$	101204910	$9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6-5*(4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$
93883923	$(9-8-7^6*(5-43))*21$	101449539	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*43-21)$
93883974	$9*8-7^6*(5-43)*21$	101449755	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*43+2+1)$
93884061	$-9+(8-7^6*(5-43))*21$	101449917	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*43+2+1)$
93884079	$9+(8-7^6*(5-43))*21$	101644173	$(-9+8*(7^6-5)*4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
93884259	$(9+8-7^6*(5-43))*21$	101644397	$9*(8*(7^6-5)*4*3-2)-1$
93885414	$(9*8-7^6*(5-43))*21$	101644399	$9*(8*(7^6-5)*4*3+2)+1$
94187025	$9/((8+7)*(6^{\wedge}5/4-3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$	101644433	$9*(8*(7^6-5)*4*3+2)-1$
94366377	$-9*(8*(76-5*4^3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	101644435	$9*(8*(7^6-5)*4*3+2)+1$
94368815	$9*8*(-7*6+5*4^3^{\wedge}2)-1$	101644659	$(9+8*(7^6-5)*4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
94368817	$9*8*(-7*6+5*4^3^{\wedge}2)+1$	101647953	$(-9+(8/7^{\wedge}6-5)*4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
94374863	$9*8*(7*6+5*4^3^{\wedge}2)-1$	101648439	$(9+(8/7^{\wedge}6-5)*4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
94374865	$9*8*(7*6+5*4^3^{\wedge}2)+1$	101648689	$9+8*((7^6*5-4-3)*2-1)$
94377303	$9*(8*(76+5*4^3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	101648785	$9+8*((7^6*5+4+3)*2-1)$
94377321	$9*(8*(76+5*4^3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	101649033	$(-9+(8/7^{\wedge}6-5)*4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
94497841	$9/((8+7)*6^{\wedge}5/4+3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$	101649519	$(9+(8/7^{\wedge}6-5)*4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
94770225	$(9/((8+7)*(6^{\wedge}5/4+3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$	101652813	$(-9+8*(7^6+5)*4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
94921632	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	101653037	$9*(8*(7^6+5)*4*3-2)-1$
94922118	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	101653039	$9*(8*(7^6+5)*4*3-2)+1$
95296266	$-9*(8+(7^6*5+4)*(3-21))$	101653073	$9*(8*(7^6+5)*4*3+2)-1$
95659359	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*6/54+3)-21$	101653075	$9*(8*(7^6+5)*4*3+2)+1$
95659401	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*6/54+3)+21$	101653299	$(9+8*(7^6+5)*4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
96001227	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5+43)-21)$	101711493	$9+(8+76*5)*(4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$
96001941	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5+43)+21)$	101712251	$-9+(8+76*5)*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$
96206481	$(-9+8*(7*6+5))*(4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$	101712269	$9+(8+76*5)*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$
96207215	$(-9+8*(7*6+5))*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$	101741427	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*(5-(4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
96354450	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+43^2)-1)$	102001326	$(9+8)*(7^6*(54-3)-21)$
96354468	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+43^2)+1)$	102119332	$98*7^6*(5+4-3/21)$
96354629	$98+7^6/5*((4^3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	102119341	$9+8*7^6*(5*43/2+1)$
96472189	$9+8*7^6*5*(43/2-1)$	102161250	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
97517205	$9-(8-76*5)*(4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$	102330000	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$
97517931	$-9-(8-76*5)*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$	102331917	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*(5+(4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
97517949	$9-(8-76*5)*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$	102335616	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$
98814399	$-9+8*(7^6*5-4^3)*21$	102335634	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$
98814417	$9+8*(7^6*5-4^3)*21$	102341250	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
98817747	$(-9+8*(7^6*5-43))*21$	102380625	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(3+21))$
98818125	$(9+8*(7^6*5-43))*21$	102396933	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
98823993	$9+8*(7^6*5-4-3)*21$	102398067	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)*21)$
98824434	$9+(8*(7^6*5-4)-3)*21$	102414375	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3-21))$
98824560	$9+(8*(7^6*5-4)+3)*21$	102498287	$(-9-8)*((7-6*5)*4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$
98824945	$9+8*(7^6*5-4/3)*21$	102498321	$(-9-8)*((7-6*5)*4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$
98825001	$9+8*(7^6*5-4+3)*21$	102498561	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*3-21)$
98825133	$(-9+8/7^{\wedge}6-6*5*(4+3))*(2+1)$	102513125	$9*(8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
102513561	$9^*((8+7)^6-5^4/3-21)$	104317570	$98^*((7^6+5^4)^3-2-1)$
102513939	$9^*((8+7)^6-5^4/3+21)$	104317766	$98^*((7^6+5^4)^3-2+1)$
102517311	$9^*((8+7)^6+5^4/3-21)$	104321250	$9^*((8+7)^6+5^4*321)$
102517689	$9^*((8+7)^6+5^4/3+21)$	104576888	$(9/(-8+7^6*(5^4)^3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
102518125	$9^*(8+7)^6+5^4*(3+2-1)$	104576890	$(9/(8+7^6*(5^4)^3+2))^{\wedge}-1$
102532689	$9^*((8+7)^6+5^4*3+21)$	104603034	$(9/(8+7^6*((5^4)^3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$
102616875	$9^*((8+7)^6-5^4*(3-21))$	106167924	$9+(87-6)^5*(4^3-2-1)$
102633183	$9^*((8+7)^6+(5^4-3)*21)$	106168248	$9+(87-6)^5*(5^4-3-2-1)$
102634317	$9^*((8+7)^6+(5^4+3)*21)$	106168410	$9+(87-6)^5*(5^4+3+2+1)$
102650625	$9^*((8+7)^6+5^4*(3+21))$	106168734	$9+(87-6)^5*(4^3-2+1)$
102690000	$9^*((8+7)^6+5^4*(32-1))$	106232175	$(-9-8+(7^6-5)^4)^3*21$
102695616	$9^*((8+7)^6+5^4*32-1)$	106232355	$-9-(8-(7^6-5)^4)^3*21$
102695634	$9^*((8+7)^6+5^4*32+1)$	106232373	$9-(8-(7^6-5)^4)^3*21$
102701250	$9^*((8+7)^6+5^4*(32+1))$	106232511	$(-9+8+(7^6-5)^4)^3*21$
102707505	$9^*(-8+7^6*(5+43)^2+1)$	106232553	$(9-8+(7^6-5)^4)^3*21$
102707649	$9^*(8+7^6*((5+43)^2+1))$	106232691	$-9+(8+(7^6-5)^4)^3*21$
102870000	$9^*((8+7)^6+5^4*3*21)$	106232709	$9+(8+(7^6-5)^4)^3*21$
103049253	$9^8*(76/54)^3/2+1$	106232889	$(9+8+(7^6-5)^4)^3*21$
103215070	$98^*((7^6-5^4)^3-2-1)$	106241205	$(-9-8+(7^6+5)^4)^3*21$
103215266	$98^*((7^6-5^4)^3-2+1)$	106241385	$-9-(8-(7^6+5)^4)^3*21$
103718692	$98^*((7^6-54)^3-2-1)$	106241403	$9-(8-(7^6+5)^4)^3*21$
103718888	$98^*((7^6-54)^3-2+1)$	106241541	$(-9+8+(7^6+5)^4)^3*21$
103748680	$98^*((7^6-5^4)^3-2-1)$	106241583	$(9-8+(7^6+5)^4)^3*21$
103748876	$98^*((7^6-5^4)^3-2+1)$	106241721	$-9+(8+(7^6+5)^4)^3*21$
103758382	$98^*((7^6-5-4)^3-2-1)$	106241739	$9+(8+(7^6+5)^4)^3*21$
103758578	$98^*((7^6-5-4)^3-2+1)$	106241919	$(9+8+(7^6+5)^4)^3*21$
103760244	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)-3*21)$	106288199	$9^8*(76/54/3+2)-1$
103761910	$98^*((7^6-5)^4*(4+3+2)-1)$	106288201	$9^8*(76/54/3+2)+1$
103762106	$98^*((7^6-5)^4*(4+3+2)+1)$	106693664	$(9^8-7^6/5^4-4)^3*(-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
103763184	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)-32-1)$	106812479	$9^8+7^6*(543-2+1)$
103763281	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)-32)-1$	107047777	$9^8+7^6*(543+2-1)$
103763282	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)-32)^{\wedge}1$	107283075	$9^8+7^6*(543+2+1)$
103763283	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)-32)+1$	107616718	$((9^8-7^6)^5+43)/2-1$
103763380	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)-32+1)$	107616928	$(9^8+7^6)^5+43)/2-1$
103763772	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	108000711	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54-3*21)$
103764066	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)-3-21)$	108001221	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54-32-1)$
103764654	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)+3-21)$	108001237	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54-32)-1$
103765438	$98^*((7^6-5+4)^3-2-1)$	108001238	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54-32)^{\wedge}1$
103765634	$98^*((7^6-5+4)^3-2+1)$	108001239	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54-32)+1$
103766103	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)-3)-21$	108001255	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54-32+1)$
103766145	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)-3)+21$	108001374	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54-3-21)$
103766345	$9^*(-8+7^6*(6-5+4+3)^2)-1$	108001476	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54+3-21)$
103766347	$9^*(-8+7^6*(6-5+4+3)^2)+1$	108001701	$9^*(-8+7^6*(54-3)^2-1)$
103766369	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)-3/2+1)$	108001752	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54-3)+21$
103766489	$9^*(8+7^6*(6-5+4+3)^2)-1$	108001812	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54+3)-21$
103766491	$9^*(8+7^6*(6-5+4+3)^2)+1$	108001917	$9^*((8+7^6*(54-3))^2-2-1)$
103766691	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)+3)-21$	108002088	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54-3+21)$
103766733	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)+3)+21$	108002190	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54+3+21)$
103766761	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	108002309	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54+32-1)$
103766810	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)+3+2-1)$	108002325	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54+32)-1$
103767202	$98^*((7^6+5-4)^3-2-1)$	108002326	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54+32)^{\wedge}1$
103767398	$98^*((7^6+5-4)^3-2+1)$	108002327	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54+32)+1$
103768182	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)-3+21)$	108002343	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54+32+1)$
103768770	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)+3+21)$	108002853	$(9+8)^*(7^6*54+3*21)$
103769064	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	108236873	$(9-8*7^6*5)^*(4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
103769456	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)+32-1)$	108237287	$(-9-8*7^6*5)^*(4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
103769553	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)+32)-1$	110097645	$(-9+8^7/6)^*((5^4+3)/2+1)$
103769554	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)+32)^{\wedge}1$	110099913	$(-9+8^7/(6/5))^*(4^3-2+1)$
103769555	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)+32)+1$	110100069	$9+(8+76)^5*(4^3-2-1)$
103769652	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)+32+1)$	110100387	$-9+(8+76)^5*(5^4-3-2-1)$
103770926	$98^*((7^6+5)^4*(4+3+2)+1)$	110100405	$9+(8+76)^5*(5^4+3-2-1)$
103772592	$98^*(7^6*(5+4)+3*21)$	110100573	$9+(8+76)^5*(5^4+3+2+1)$
103774258	$98^*((7^6+5+4)^3-2-1)$	110100891	$-9+(8+76)^5*(4^3+2+1)$
103774454	$98^*((7^6+5+4)^3-2+1)$	110100909	$9+(8+76)^5*(4^3+2+1)$
103783960	$98^*((7^6+5^4)^3-2-1)$	110101047	$(9+8^7/(6/5))^*(4^3-2+1)$
103784156	$98^*((7^6+5^4)^3-2+1)$	110103315	$(9+8^7/6)^*((5^4+3)/2+1)$
103813948	$98^*((7^6+54)^3-2-1)$	110109288	$(-9+(8+7)^6)^*(5^4/3+2+1)$
103814144	$98^*((7^6+54)^3-2+1)$	110109462	$(9+(8+7)^6)^*(5^4/3+2+1)$
103826340	$9^*(8+7)^6+5^4*(4^3-2-1)$	110156203	$(-9+8^7)^*(6^5+4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
103826350	$9^*(8+7)^6+5^4*(4^3+2+1)$	110156297	$(-9+8^7)^*(6^5+4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
104119293	$-9^*(8+7^6*5^4*(4/3-21))$	110343175	$(9+8)/(7/((6^5+4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1))$
104119437	$9^*(8-7^6*5^4*(4/3-21))$	110657826	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^4*3-2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
110775924	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6) * (5^{\wedge}4 * 3+2-1)$	114031692	$9-87 * (6-5 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
110886839	$9 * (-8+(7 * 6+5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) -1$	114032022	$-9-87 * (6-5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
110886841	$9 * (-8+(7 * 6+5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	114032040	$9-87 * (6-5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
110886983	$9 * (8+(7 * 6+5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) -1$	114032214	$9-87 * (6-5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
110886985	$9 * (8+(7 * 6+5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	114032544	$-9-87 * (6-5 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
110894022	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6) * (5^{\wedge}4 * 3+2+1)$	114032562	$9-87 * (6-5 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
111111112	$(9 / (8+(7-6+5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	114032736	$9+87 * (6+5 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
111166137	$9 * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5-4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	114033084	$9+87 * (6+5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
111166281	$9 * (8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5-4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	114033258	$9+87 * (6+5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
111168666	$9 * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5-43) * 21)$	114033588	$-9+87 * (6+5 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
111170106	$9 * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5-43) * 21)$	114033606	$9+87 * (6+5 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
111170250	$9 * (8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5-43) * 21)$	114353532	$(9 * 8-7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (3-21)$
111171690	$9 * (8+7^{\wedge}6 * 5-43) * 21$	114354522	$(9+8-7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (3-21)$
111176910	$9 * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5-4-3) * 21)$	114354675	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (3-21)$
111177981	$9 * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5-4/3) * 21)$	114354693	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (3-21)$
111178044	$9 * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5-4+3) * 21)$	114354711	$9 * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 54-3) * 2+1)$
111178422	$9 * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5+4-3) * 21)$	114354801	$9 * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 54+3) * 2-1)$
111178485	$9 * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5+4/3) * 21)$	114354909	$9 * ((8+7^{\wedge}6 * 54-3) * 2-1)$
111179556	$9 * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5+4+3) * 21)$	114354927	$9 * ((8+7^{\wedge}6 * 54-3) * 2+1)$
111184920	$9 * (-8+7^{\wedge}6 * 5+43) * 21$	114354981	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (3-21)$
111186360	$9 * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5+43) * 21)$	114355035	$9 * ((8+7^{\wedge}6 * 54+3) * 2+1)$
111186504	$9 * (8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5+43) * 21)$	114355134	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (-3+21)$
111187944	$9 * (8+7^{\wedge}6 * 5+43) * 21$	114356124	$(9 * 8+7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (-3+21)$
111190329	$9 * (-8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5+4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	115051833	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6+5^{\wedge}4 * 321)$
111190473	$9 * (8+(7^{\wedge}6 * 5+4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	115283378	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 5-4^{\wedge}3) * 2-1)$
111295882	$-9 * (8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4+321))$	115283574	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 5-4^{\wedge}3) * 2+1)$
111295937	$-9-8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4+321)$	115287494	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 5-43) * 2-1)$
111295953	$-9+8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4+321)$	115287690	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 5-43) * 2+1)$
111295955	$9-8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4+321)$	115304350	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 5+43) * 2-1)$
111295971	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4+321)$	115304546	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 5+43) * 2+1)$
111296026	$9 * 8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4+321)$	115308466	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 5+4^{\wedge}3) * 2-1)$
111440583	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6-5^{\wedge}4 * 321)$	115308662	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 5+4^{\wedge}3) * 2+1)$
112941477	$(9+(8-7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * 4^{\wedge}3) * (-2-1)$	115371881	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6) * (54/32+1)$
112941531	$(9-(8-7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * 4^{\wedge}3) * (2+1)$	115676991	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 * 6^{\wedge}5-5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 2) -1$
112942281	$9+8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5-4) * (3+21)$	115753803	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4-3 * 2-1)$
112942942	$-9+8+7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * (2+1)$	116001897	$(9+8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 * 4 * 3-2) -1)$
112942953	$9+(8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5-4) * (3+21)$	116001931	$(9+8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 * 4 * 3-2)+1)$
112943138	$98+7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * (2+1)$	116106750	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4-3-2+1)$
112943817	$9+8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5+4) * (3+21)$	116342048	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4-3+2-1)$
112944549	$(-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * 4^{\wedge}3) * (2+1)$	116472438	$9 * (-8+7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (43-21))$
112944603	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * 4^{\wedge}3) * (2+1)$	116702857	$9+8 * (7^{\wedge}6-5) * 4 * (32-1)$
112984055	$-9+8^{\wedge}7 * (7-6+5) * (432-1)$	116712777	$9+8 * (7^{\wedge}6+5) * 4 * (32-1)$
112984073	$9+8^{\wedge}7 * (7-6+5) * (432-1)$	116812644	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4+3-2+1)$
113045583	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * 6+5^{\wedge}4 * 321$	116920468	$-98 * (7^{\wedge}6-5 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
113060583	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6-5^{\wedge}4 * (32+1))$	116920860	$-98 * (7^{\wedge}6-5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
113066199	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6-5^{\wedge}4 * 32-1)$	116921056	$-98 * (7^{\wedge}6-5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
113066217	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6-5^{\wedge}4 * 32+1)$	116921448	$-98 * (7^{\wedge}6-5 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
113071833	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6-5^{\wedge}4 * (32-1))$	117047942	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4+3+2-1)$
113111208	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6-5^{\wedge}4 * (3+21))$	117177930	$9-(8-7 * 65) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
113127516	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6-(5^{\wedge}4+3) * 21)$	117178806	$-9-(8-7 * 65) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
113128650	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6-(5^{\wedge}4-3) * 21)$	117178824	$9-(8-7 * 65) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
113144958	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6+5^{\wedge}4 * (3-21))$	117400889	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4+3 * 2+1)$
113229144	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6-5^{\wedge}4 * 3-21)$	117648775	$(-9+8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * (4 * 3 * 2+1)$
113244144	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6-5^{\wedge}4 / 3-21)$	117649225	$(9+8 / 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * (4 * 3 * 2+1)$
113244522	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6-5^{\wedge}4 / 3+21)$	118001896	$(-9-8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5-4^{\wedge}3)+2+1)$
113247894	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6+5^{\wedge}4 / 3-21)$	118001930	$(-9-8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5-4^{\wedge}3)+2-1)$
113248272	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6+5^{\wedge}4 / 3+21)$	118001964	$(-9-8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5-4^{\wedge}3)-2+1)$
113263272	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6+5^{\wedge}4 * 3+21)$	118001998	$(-9-8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5-4^{\wedge}3)-2-1)$
113347458	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6-5^{\wedge}4 * (3-21))$	118237173	$9 * (-8+7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4/3+21))$
113363766	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6+(5^{\wedge}4-3) * 21)$	118237317	$9 * (8+7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4/3+21))$
113364900	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6+(5^{\wedge}4+3) * 21)$	118588680	$(-9 * 8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43)) * 21$
113381208	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6+5^{\wedge}4 * (3+21))$	118589835	$(-9-8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43)) * 21$
113420583	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6+5^{\wedge}4 * (32-1))$	118590015	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43)) * 21$
113426199	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6+5^{\wedge}4 * 32-1)$	118590033	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43)) * 21$
113426217	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6+5^{\wedge}4 * 32+1)$	118590171	$(-9+8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43)) * 21$
113431833	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6+5^{\wedge}4 * (32+1))$	118590175	$-9-8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43) * 21$
113446833	$9 * 8^{\wedge}7 * 6+5^{\wedge}4 * 321$	118590209	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43) * 21$
113508343	$-9+8^{\wedge}7 * (7-6+5) * (432+1)$	118590213	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43)) * 21$
113508361	$9+8^{\wedge}7 * (7-6+5) * (432+1)$	118590351	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43)) * 21$
114001524	$(9-8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5+4+3) -21)$	118590369	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43)) * 21$
114001898	$(-9-8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5-4^{\wedge}3+2) -1)$	118590549	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43)) * 21$
114002238	$(9+8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5+4+3)+21)$	118591704	$(9 * 8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43)) * 21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
119274967	$-98+7*65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	126002058	$(-9+8+7\wedge 6*(54-3))*21$
119275163	$98+7*65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	126002100	$(9-8+7\wedge 6*(54-3))*21$
119275415	$-98+7*(65*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	126002238	$-9+(8+7\wedge 6*(54-3))*21$
119275625	$98+7*(65*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	126002256	$9+(8+7\wedge 6*(54-3))*21$
119275877	$-98+7*65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	126002436	$(9+8+7\wedge 6*(54-3))*21$
119276073	$98+7*65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	126003591	$(9*8+7\wedge 6*(54-3))*21$
119531393	$9-8*7\wedge 6*(5-4*(32+1))$	126660105	$9\wedge 8*(7*6/(-5-4))^3+2+1$
119572100	$(9\wedge 8-765)*((4/3)^2+1)$	126825720	$98*(7\wedge 6*(5+4^3/2)+1)$
119576350	$(9\wedge 8+765)*((4/3)^2+1)$	127059975	$9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5-4)-3)*(2+1)$
119766610	$-9*8-7\wedge 6*(5-4\wedge(3+2)+1)$	127060037	$9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5-4)*3-2)-1$
119766754	$9*8-7\wedge 6*(5-4\wedge(3+2)+1)$	127060039	$9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5-4)*3-2)+1$
120001827	$(9+8)*(7\wedge 6*5*4-3)*(2+1)$	127060073	$9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5-4)*3+2)-1$
120001908	$-9*8-7\wedge 6*(5-4\wedge(3+2)-1)$	127060075	$9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5-4)*3+2)+1$
120001929	$(9+8)*(7\wedge 6*5*4*3-2-1)$	127060137	$9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5-4)+3)*(2+1)$
120001945	$(9+8)*(7\wedge 6*5*4*3-2)-1$	127060299	$(9+8*(7\wedge 6*5-4))*3\wedge(2+1)$
120001946	$(9+8)*(7\wedge 6*5*4*3-2)\wedge 1$	127060847	$9*(-8+7\wedge 6*5*4*3*2)-1$
120001947	$(9+8)*(7\wedge 6*5*4*3-2)+1$	127060849	$9*(-8+7\wedge 6*5*4*3*2)+1$
120002013	$(9+8)*(7\wedge 6*5*4*3+2)-1$	127060991	$9*(8+7\wedge 6*5*4*3*2)-1$
120002014	$(9+8)*(7\wedge 6*5*4*3+2)/1$	127060993	$9*(8+7\wedge 6*5*4*3*2)+1$
120002015	$(9+8)*(7\wedge 6*5*4*3+2)+1$	127061541	$(-9+8*(7\wedge 6*5+4))*3\wedge(2+1)$
120002031	$(9+8)*(7\wedge 6*5*4*3+2)+1$	127061703	$9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5+4)-3)*(2+1)$
120002052	$9*8-7\wedge 6*(5-4\wedge(3+2)-1)$	127061765	$9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5+4)*3-2)-1$
120002133	$(9+8)*(7\wedge 6*5*4+3)*(2+1)$	127061767	$9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5+4)*3-2)+1$
120707793	$9*(-8+7\wedge 6*(54+3)*2-1)$	127061801	$9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5+4)*3+2)-1$
120707811	$9*(-8+7\wedge 6*(54+3)*2+1)$	127061803	$9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5+4)*3+2)+1$
120708009	$9*((8+7\wedge 6*(54+3))*2-1)$	127061865	$9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5+4)+3)*(2+1)$
120708027	$9*((8+7\wedge 6*(54+3))*2+1)$	127087953	$9\wedge 8*-7+65\wedge 4*(3+21)$
120943100	$-9*8+7\wedge 6*(5+4\wedge(3+2)-1)$	127165756	$9\wedge 8+7\wedge 6*5*((4*3)^2-1)$
120943244	$9*8+7\wedge 6*(5+4\wedge(3+2)-1)$	127363652	$9\wedge 8+7\wedge 6*(5*(4*3)^2-1)$
121056800	$98*(7/(6\wedge 5+4))\wedge(-3+2-1)$	127734048	$(-9+8*7*6)*5\wedge 4\wedge(3/2)-1$
121178398	$-9*8+7\wedge 6*(5+4\wedge(3+2)+1)$	127734702	$(-9+8*7*6)*(5\wedge 4\wedge(3/2)+1)$
121178542	$9*8+7\wedge 6*(5+4\wedge(3+2)+1)$	127871650	$9\wedge 8+7\wedge 6*(5*(4*3)^2+1)$
121305790	$98*((7/(6\wedge 5+4*3))\wedge-2-1)$	127996621	$(9+8)*((7\wedge 6-5)*4\wedge 3-2-1)$
121372218	$9*(8+7*65)*((4^3\wedge 2-1)$	127996655	$(9+8)*((7\wedge 6-5)*4\wedge 3-2+1)$
121373126	$-9+(8+7*65)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	127996689	$(9+8)*((7\wedge 6-5)*4\wedge 3+2-1)$
121373144	$9+(8+7*65)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	127996723	$(9+8)*((7\wedge 6-5)*4\wedge 3+2+1)$
121617853	$9/(87-6/(5+4))\wedge-3*21$	128007501	$(9+8)*((7\wedge 6+5)*4\wedge 3-2-1)$
121634361	$9-8*(7-65)*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	128007535	$(9+8)*((7\wedge 6+5)*4\wedge 3-2+1)$
121634729	$(-9+8\wedge 7*6)*(5*4/3+2+1)$	128007569	$(9+8)*((7\wedge 6+5)*4\wedge 3+2-1)$
121634815	$-9-8*((7-65)*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	128007603	$(9+8)*((7\wedge 6+5)*4\wedge 3+2+1)$
121634817	$9-8*((7-65)*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	128024034	$-9+(8*7/(6/54))\wedge 3-21$
121635271	$-9-8*(7-65)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	128024094	$9+(8*7/(6/54))\wedge 3+21$
121635289	$9-8*(7-65)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	128342246	$9\wedge 8+7\wedge 6*5*((4*3)^2+1)$
121896504	$9+(87+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	128372526	$9\wedge 8*((7+6)*(-5-4)\wedge-3+2+1)$
121896858	$-9+(87+6)*(5*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	128448796	$-98*(7+6-5*(4^3\wedge 2-1))$
121896876	$9+(87+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	128449188	$-98*(7+6-5*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
121897062	$9+(87+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	128449384	$-98*(7+6-5*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
121897416	$-9+(87+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	128449776	$-98*(7+6-5*(4^3\wedge 2+1))$
121897434	$9+(87+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	128449972	$-98*(7-6-5*(4^3\wedge 2+1))$
122001996	$(-9-8)*(7\wedge 6*(5-4\wedge 3-2)+1)$	128450364	$-98*(7-6-5*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
122002030	$(-9-8)*(7\wedge 6*(5-4\wedge 3-2)-1)$	128450952	$-98*(7-6-5*(4^3\wedge 2+1))$
123046802	$-9*(8-7*(6-5+4)\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1$	128452324	$98*(7+6+5*(4^3\wedge 2+1))$
123046804	$-9*(8-7*(6-5+4)\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1$	128454186	$98*(7*6+5*(4^3\wedge 2-1))$
123046946	$9*(8+7*(6-5+4)\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1$	128454578	$98*(7*6+5*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
123046948	$9*(8+7*(6-5+4)\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1$	128454774	$98*(7*6+5*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
123996759	$(9+8)*((7\wedge 6-5)*(4^3-2)-1)$	128455166	$98*(7*6+5*(4^3\wedge 2+1))$
123996793	$(9+8)*((7\wedge 6-5)*(4^3-2)+1)$	128993283	$(9\wedge 8-765*4^3)*(2+1)$
124002029	$(9+8)*(7\wedge 6*(5*4*3+2)-1)$	129022065	$9\wedge 8*((7-6-(5+4)\wedge-3)*2+1)$
124002063	$(9+8)*(7\wedge 6*(5*4*3+2)+1)$	129091143	$(9\wedge 8-76*5*4^3)*(2+1)$
124007299	$(9+8)*((7\wedge 6+5)*(4^3-2)-1)$	129103227	$(9\wedge 8-76*5*4^3)*(2+1)$
124007333	$(9+8)*((7\wedge 6+5)*(4^3-2)+1)$	129112623	$(9\wedge 8-765*4*3)*(2+1)$
124232073	$9+8*(7\wedge 6-5)*4*(32+1)$	129118986	$(9\wedge 8-(7+6)*5*4^3*(2+1))$
124238013	$9+(8*7\wedge 6+5)*4*(32+1)$	129124098	$(9\wedge 8-765*(4+3))*(2+1)$
124242633	$9+8*(7\wedge 6+5)*4*(32+1)$	129128535	$(9\wedge 8-76*(54-3))*(2+1)$
124354984	$(9\wedge 8-765)*(4-3\wedge-2-1)$	129129219	$(9\wedge 8-76*(5+43))*(2+1)$
124359404	$(9\wedge 8+765)*(4-3\wedge-2-1)$	129129714	$(9\wedge 8-(76+5)*4^3*(2+1))$
124518305	$(-9+8*(7+6))*(5*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	129130875	$(9\wedge 8-(7+65)*4^3*(2+1))$
124518495	$(-9+8*(7+6))*(5*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	129131499	$(9\wedge 8+76*(5-43))*(2+1)$
126000567	$(-9*8+7\wedge 6*(54-3))*21$	129132603	$(9\wedge 8-7*6*5*4*3)*(2+1)$
126001722	$(-9-8+7\wedge 6*(54-3))*21$	129132681	$(9\wedge 8+(7-65)*4^3*(2+1))$
126001902	$-9-(8-7\wedge 6*(54-3))*21$	129133242	$(9\wedge 8-(765+4)*3*(2+1))$
126001920	$9-(8-7\wedge 6*(54-3))*21$	129133314	$(9\wedge 8-(765-4)*3*(2+1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
129134214	$(9^8 - (7+654)^3)^*(2+1)$	133920752	$(9^8 - 765)^*(4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$
129134340	$(9^8 + (7-654)^3)^*(2+1)$	133925512	$(9^8 + 765)^*(4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$
129135753	$(9^8 - 7^6 * 5^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$	133955073	$(-9+8^*(7+6)^5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
129136059	$(9^8 - 76^*54/3)^*(2+1)$	133956095	$(-9+8^*(7+6)^5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
129136761	$(9^8 - 7^6 * (5+4)^3)^*(2+1)$	134002194	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$
129137103	$(9^8 - 765^*4/3)^*(2+1)$	134002228	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3-2)+1)$
129137265	$(9^8 - 7^6 * (5^*4+3))^*(2+1)$	134472735	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^*(32+1)))$
129137391	$(9^8 - 7^*(6+5)^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	134479287	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-65^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
129137580	$(9^8 - 7^*(6^*5^4+3))^*(2+1)$	134480457	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-65^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
129137706	$(9^8 - 7^*(6^*5^4-3))^*(2+1)$	134741824	$9^*(87/(6^{\wedge}5-4))^{\wedge}3 * 21$
129137823	$(9^8 - (7+6)^5 * 4^3)^*(2+1)$	134765280	$(9+8^*7^6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
129138021	$(9^8 - 7^*(6^*5+4)^3)^*(2+1)$	134765970	$(9+8^*7^6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
129138237	$(9^8 - (7^6 * 5+4)^3)^*(2+1)$	135283537	$9^8 + (7^*(6-5^4))^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
129138471	$(9^8 - (7^6+5)^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	135527940	$9+(87^*6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
129139323	$(9^8 - 7^6 * 5^*4/3)^*(2+1)$	135528401	$(-9+8^7)^*((6+5)^4 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
129139335	$(9^8 + (7-6^*5)^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	135528495	$(-9+8^7)^*((6+5)^4 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
129139502	$(9^8 - (7+654)/3)^*(2+1)$	135528956	$-9+(87^*6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
129139516	$(9^8 + (7-654)/3)^*(2+1)$	135528974	$9+(87^*6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
129140810	$(9^8 - (7-654)/3)^*(2+1)$	135539703	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^4)^*32-1)$
129140824	$(9^8 + (7+654)/3)^*(2+1)$	135539721	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^4)^*32+1)$
129140991	$(9^8 - (7-6^*5)^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	136314313	$9-8^*(7-65^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
129141003	$(9^8 + 7^6 * 5^*4/3)^*(2+1)$	136314425	$9+8^*(7+65^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
129141855	$(9^8 + (7^6+5)^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	136315335	$-9-8^*(7-65^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
129142089	$(9^8 + (7^6 * 5+4)^3)^*(2+1)$	136315353	$9-8^*(7-65^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
129142305	$(9^8 + 7^*(6^*5+4)^3)^*(2+1)$	136315447	$-9+8^*(7+65^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
129142503	$(9^8 + (7+6)^5 * 4^3)^*(2+1)$	136590417	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4^*(32-1)))$
129142620	$(9^8 + 7^*(6^*5^4-3))^*(2+1)$	136836045	$9-87^*6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
129142746	$(9^8 + 7^*(6^*5^4+3))^*(2+1)$	136836480	$9-87^*(6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
129142935	$(9^8 + 7^*(6+5)^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	136836636	$-9-87^*(6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
129143061	$(9^8 + 7^6 * (5^*4+3))^*(2+1)$	136836654	$9-87^*(6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
129143223	$(9^8 + 765^*4/3)^*(2+1)$	136837089	$9-87^*6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
129143565	$(9^8 + 7^6 * (5+4)^3)^*(2+1)$	136838574	$-9^*(8+(7-65)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
129144267	$(9^8 + 76^*54/3)^*(2+1)$	136839618	$-9^*(8+(7-65)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
129144573	$(9^8 + 7^6 * 5^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$	136839762	$9^*(8-(7-65)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
129145986	$(9^8 - (7-654)^3)^*(2+1)$	136841265	$9+87^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
129146112	$(9^8 + (7+654)^3)^*(2+1)$	136841682	$-9+87^*(6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
129147012	$(9^8 + (765-4)^3)^*(2+1)$	136841700	$9+87^*(6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
129147084	$(9^8 + (765+4)^3)^*(2+1)$	136841874	$9+87^*(6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
129147645	$(9^8 - (7-65)^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	136842291	$-9+87^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
129147723	$(9^8 + 7^6 * 5^*4^3)^*(2+1)$	136842309	$9+87^*6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
129148827	$(9^8 - 76^*(5-43))^*(2+1)$	136930623	$9^8 - 7^{\wedge}6^*(5-43)^*21$
129149451	$(9^8 + (7+65)^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	137395278	$9/8^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^3)/2-1)$
129150612	$(9^8 + (76+5)^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	138002226	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-2-1)$
129151107	$(9^8 + 76^*(5+43))^*(2+1)$	138002260	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-2+1)$
129151791	$(9^8 + 76^*(54-3))^*(2+1)$	138002294	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+2-1)$
129156228	$(9^8 + 765^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$	138002328	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+2+1)$
129161340	$(9^8 + (7+6)^5 * 43)^*(2+1)$	138149370	$9+(87^*6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
129167703	$(9^8 + 765^*4^3)^*(2+1)$	138150424	$9+(87^*6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
129177099	$(9^8 + 76^*54^3)^*(2+1)$	138347286	$98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^4 * 3-21)$
129189183	$(9^8 + 76^*5^4 * 3)^*(2+1)$	138349295	$98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^4 * 3-2^{\wedge}1)$
129258261	$9^8 * ((7-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$	138349393	$98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^4 * 3+2^{\wedge}1)$
129287043	$(9^8 + 765^*4^{\wedge}3)^*(2+1)$	138351402	$98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^4 * 3+21)$
129311424	$9^*(8/7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(43^{\wedge}2-1)$	138355175	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4+3)-2^{\wedge}1)$
129349440	$9^*(8/7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(43^{\wedge}2-1)$	138355273	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4+3)+2^{\wedge}1)$
129907800	$9^8 * ((7+6)^*(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$	138355322	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4+3)+2-1)$
130002128	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4+3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	138355518	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4+3)+2+1)$
130002162	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4+3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	138355968	$9+(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3)^*21$
131290632	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^4 * (32-1))$	138359046	$98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^4 * 3-21)$
131301792	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^4 * (32-1))$	138361055	$98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^4 * 3-2^{\wedge}1)$
131620221	$9^8 * (7^6 / (5+4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$	138361153	$98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^4 * 3+2^{\wedge}1)$
131766897	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4-32)-1)$	138363162	$98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^4 * 3+21)$
131996551	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$	138673647	$(9+8^*(7+6)^5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
131996585	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	138674705	$(9+8^*(7+6)^5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
132007771	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$	139401252	$9^8 + 7^{\wedge}6 / 5^*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
132007805	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	139531714	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}4/32-1)$
132087744	$-9^*(8^*(7^*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1))$	139761000	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^4 * (32+1))$
132087807	$-9^*(8^*(7^*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1))$	139767021	$-9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5-43/2)-1))$
132087825	$-9^*(8^*(7^*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1))$	139772880	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^4 * (32+1))$
132087888	$-9^*(8^*(7^*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1))$	139979672	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
132153264	$9^*8^*(7^*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	139980064	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
132153345	$9^*(8^*(7^*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1))$	139980260	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
133649273	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6^*(5-(4+3)^*21)$	139980652	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
140002293	$(9+8)*(7^6*5*(4^3+2)-1)$	149878358	$98*((7^6-5)*(4+3^2)-1)$
140002327	$(9+8)*(7^6*5*(4^3+2)+1)$	149878554	$98*((7^6-5)*(4+3^2)+1)$
140824341	$(-9*8+7^6*(54+3))*21$	149884728	$98*(7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1)$
140825496	$(-9-8+7^6*(54+3))*21$	149884924	$98*(7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3/2))+1)$
140825676	$-9-(8-7^6*(54+3))*21$	149891098	$98*((7^6+5)*(4+3^2)-1)$
140825694	$9-(8-7^6*(54+3))*21$	149891294	$98*((7^6+5)*(4+3^2)+1)$
140825832	$(-9+8+7^6*(54+3))*21$	150355350	$-9*(8+7^6*(5-(4+3)*21))$
140825836	$-9-8+7^6*(54+3)*21$	150355494	$9*(8-7^6*(5-(4+3)*21))$
140825852	$-9+8+7^6*(54+3)*21$	150589697	$9+8*((7^6*5-4)*32-1)$
140825854	$9-8+7^6*(54+3)*21$	150589713	$9+8*((7^6*5-4)*32+1)$
140825870	$9+8+7^6*(54+3)*21$	150591745	$9+8*((7^6*5+4)*32-1)$
140825874	$(9-8+7^6*(54+3))*21$	150591761	$9+8*((7^6*5+4)*32+1)$
140826012	$-9+(8+7^6*(54+3))*21$	151052319	$-9-(8-(7^6-5)*4)*321$
140826030	$9+(8+7^6*(54+3))*21$	151052337	$9-(8-(7^6-5)*4)*321$
140826210	$(9+8+7^6*(54+3))*21$	151070295	$-9+(8+(7^6+5)*4)*321$
140827365	$(9*8+7^6*(54+3))*21$	151070313	$9+(8+(7^6+5)*4)*321$
142002326	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$	151414704	$98*((7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^2-1)$
142002360	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	151414900	$98*((7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^2+1)$
142804811	$(-9+8/(7/65^{\wedge}4*3))*21$	152002517	$9+8*7^6*(54*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
142805189	$(9+8/(7/65^{\wedge}4*3))*21$	152403120	$-9*8*(7^6-54)*(3-21)$
142943463	$9*(-8+7^6*54*(3/2+1))$	152466551	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)*(4^3)^2)-1$
143061193	$9+8*7^6*(5+(4+3)*21)$	152466553	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)*(4^3)^2)+1$
143370972	$9^8*((7/6-(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)*2+1)$	152466695	$9*(8+(7^6-5)*(4^3)^2)-1$
144002231	$9*8*(7^6*(5*4-3)-2)-1$	152466697	$9*(8+(7^6-5)*(4^3)^2)+1$
144002233	$9*8*(7^6*(5*4-3)-2)+1$	152471376	$(-9*8+7^6*54)*(3+21)$
144002357	$9*(8/(7^{\wedge}-6/(5*4-3))-2)-1$	152471592	$9*8*(7^6*54/3-21)$
144002395	$9*(8/(7^{\wedge}-6/(5*4-3))+2)+1$	152472696	$(-9-8+7^6*54)*(3+21)$
144002519	$9*8*(7^6*(5*4-3)+2)-1$	152472903	$-9-(8-7^6*54)*(3+21)$
144002521	$9*8*(7^6*(5*4-3)+2)+1$	152472915	$9*(8*7^6*54/3-21)$
145765053	$(98+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))*-21$	152472921	$9-(8-7^6*54)*(3+21)$
145766934	$-9-(8+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))*21$	152472969	$9*(8*(7^6*54/3-2)+1)$
145766952	$9-(8+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))*21$	152473089	$9+8*(7^6*54*3-2-1)$
145767013	$-98-7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	152473117	$9+8*(7^6*54*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
145767209	$98-7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	152473137	$9+8*(7^6*54*3+2+1)$
145767270	$-9+(8-7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))*21$	152473287	$-9+(8+7^6*54)*(3+21)$
145767288	$9+(8-7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))*21$	152473293	$9*(8*7^6*54/3+21)$
145769169	$(98-7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))*21$	152473305	$9+(8+7^6*54)*(3+21)$
145883777	$9+8*(7^6*5-4)*(32-1)$	152473512	$(9+8+7^6*54)*(3+21)$
145884481	$(-9+8*7^6*5)*(4^3/2-1)$	152474616	$9*8*(7^6*54/3+21)$
145885039	$(9+8*7^6*5)*(4^3/2-1)$	152474832	$(9*8+7^6*54)*(3+21)$
145885761	$9+8*(7^6*5+4)*(32-1)$	152479511	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)*(4^3)^2)-1$
146237609	$-98+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$	152479513	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)*(4^3)^2)+1$
146237635	$-9*8+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$	152479655	$9*(8+(7^6+5)*(4^3)^2)-1$
146237779	$9*8+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$	152479657	$9*(8+(7^6+5)*(4^3)^2)+1$
146237805	$98+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$	152481852	$-9*(8*7^6*54)*(3-21)$
146472907	$-98+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$	152543088	$-9*8*(7^6+54)*(3-21)$
146472933	$-9*8+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$	153352872	$-9*(87-65*(4^{\wedge}3)^2-1)$
146473077	$9*8+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$	153353448	$-9*(87-65*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
146473103	$98+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$	153353456	$-9*(87-65*4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$
147649397	$-98+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$	153353458	$-9*(87-65*4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$
147649423	$-9*8+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$	153353466	$-9*(87-65*4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
147649567	$9*8+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$	153353520	$-9*(8+7-65*(4^{\wedge}3)^2-1))$
147649593	$98+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$	153353646	$-9*(8-7-65*(4^{\wedge}3)^2-1))$
147884695	$-98+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$	153354042	$-9*(87-65*(4^{\wedge}3)^2+1))$
147884721	$-9*8+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$	153354096	$-9*(8+7-65*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
147884865	$9*8+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$	153354114	$-9*(8+7-65*4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
147884891	$98+7^6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$	153354167	$9*(-8+(7+6)*5*4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$
148235733	$9*((8-7^6*5)*(4-32)+1)$	153354169	$9*(-8+(7+6)*5*4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$
148237659	$-9*(8+7^6*5*(4-32)+1)$	153354222	$-9*(8-7-65*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
148695523	$9^8-7^6*(5-43*21)$	153354311	$9*(8+(7+6)*5*4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$
148897233	$9+8*(76-5)*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$	153354313	$9*(8+(7+6)*5*4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$
148897775	$-9+8*((76-5)*4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$	153354438	$9*(87+65*(4^{\wedge}3)^2-1)$
148897791	$-9+8*((76-5)*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$	153354690	$-9*(8+7-65*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1))$
148897793	$9+8*((76-5)*4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$	153354735	$9*(8*7+65*4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
148897809	$9+8*((76-5)*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$	153354816	$-9*(8-7-65*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1))$
148898369	$9+8*(76-5)*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$	153354960	$9*(8+7+65*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1))$
149296509	$9*(-8+7^6*(54*3-21))$	153355014	$9*(87+65*4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
149296653	$9*(8+7^6*(54*3-21))$	153355022	$9*(87+65*4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$
149334921	$9^8*(76/54/3+2+1)$	153355024	$9*(87+65*4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$
149421966	$(9*8+7^6)*5*(5*4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$	153355032	$9*(87+65*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
149422194	$(9*8+7^6)*5*(5*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$	153355329	$9*(8*7+65*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1))$
149872013	$9^8+7^6*(5+43*21)$	153355608	$9*(87+65*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
154136458	$-98*(7+6*(5-4^3\wedge 2+1))$	161407470	$98*((7^6-5)*(4+3)^2-1)$
154136948	$-98*(7+6*(5-4^3\wedge 2)+1)$	161407666	$98*((7^6-5)*(4+3)^2+1)$
154137144	$-98*(7+6*(5-4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	161421190	$98*((7^6+5)*(4+3)^2-1)$
154137634	$-98*(7+6*(5-4^3\wedge 2-1))$	161421386	$98*((7^6+5)*(4+3)^2+1)$
154138516	$98*(7-6*(5-4^3\wedge 2)+1)$	161636913	$9^8+7^6*(5+43)^*21$
154140574	$98*(7-6+5)*4^3\wedge 2-1$	162002601	$9*(-8+7^6*(54-3))^*(2+1)$
154140770	$98*((7-6+5)*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	162002745	$9*(8+7^6*(54-3))^*(2+1)$
154142338	$-98*(7-6*(5+4^3\wedge 2-1))$	162620925	$9^8*(7^6/54+3)-21$
154142828	$-98*(7-6*(5+4^3\wedge 2)+1)$	162620967	$9^8*(7^6/54+3)+21$
154143024	$-98*(7-6*(5+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	164119167	$9*(-8+(7^6*5-4))^*(32-1)$
154143514	$-98*(7-6*(5+4^3\wedge 2+1))$	164121399	$9*(-8+(7^6*5+4))^*(32-1)$
154144886	$98*(7+6*(5+4^3\wedge 2+1))$	164178520	$(-9+8^7)*((6-5^4\wedge 3)^2-1)$
154342675	$9^8+7^6*(5^4+321)$	164178614	$(-9+8^7)*((6-5^4\wedge 3)^2+1)$
154355489	$9+8*(7^6*(5^4*3+2)-1)$	164602270	$98*((7-6+5)^4\wedge(3/2)-1)$
154355505	$9+8*(7^6*(5^4*3+2)+1)$	164602466	$98*((7-6+5)^4\wedge(3/2)+1)$
154590786	$(98/7)^6*(5^4/32+1)$	164888559	$(9+8)*((7+6^5)*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
154844704	$98*((7+6^5\wedge 4/3)^2-1)$	164888593	$(9+8)*((7+6^5)*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
154844900	$98*((7+6^5\wedge 4/3)^2+1)$	165009498	$(9^8-765)*(4-(3^2)\wedge-1)$
155295633	$9+8*(7^6*5-4)^*(32+1)$	165015363	$(9^8+765)*(4-(3^2)\wedge-1)$
155296557	$9+(8*7^6*5-4)^*(32+1)$	165041955	$(9^8+76^5\wedge 4)^*(2+1)$
155297745	$9+8*(7^6*5+4)^*(32+1)$	166293520	$(-9+8^7)*((6+5^4\wedge 3)^2-1)$
155642940	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)*(4+3))^*21$	166293614	$(-9+8^7)*((6+5^4\wedge 3)^2+1)$
155649725	$98*(7^6*(5+4)^3/2+1)$	166590957	$(-9-8*7^6*(5-4^3))^*(2+1)$
155656170	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)*(4+3))^*21$	166591011	$(9-8*7^6*(5-4^3))^*(2+1)$
155823750	$9^8-76/(5^4-4^3-21)$	167509305	$9*(-8+(76-5)^4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1)$
155974949	$(-9-8)*(7*(6-5^4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$	167509449	$9*(8+(76-5)^4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1)$
155974983	$(-9-8)*(7*(6-5^4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$	167509935	$9*(-8+(76-5)^4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1)$
155976377	$(9+8)*(7*(6+5^4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$	167509953	$9*(-8+(76-5)^4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1)$
155976411	$(9+8)*(7*(6+5^4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$	167510583	$9*(-8+(76-5)^4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1)$
155989761	$9^8+7^6*5^4\wedge 3*(2+1)$	167510727	$9*(8+(76-5)^4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1)$
157531913	$-98-7^6*(5-4^3)^*21$	169048800	$9^8+7^6*(54-3)^*21$
157532109	$98-7^6*(5-4^3)^*21$	169413327	$9*(-8+(7^6*5-4)^3\wedge 2-1)$
157837929	$((9^8-7)^*(6+5)-4)/3-21$	169413345	$9*(-8+(7^6*5-4)^3\wedge 2+1)$
157838025	$((9^8+7)^*(6+5)+4)/3+21$	169414325	$9*(8*(7^6*5^4-3)-2)-1$
158072238	$9+(8*76-5)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	169414327	$9*(8*(7^6*5^4-3)-2)+1$
158073426	$-9+(8*76-5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	169414361	$9*(8*(7^6*5^4-3)+2)-1$
158073444	$9+(8*76-5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	169414363	$9*(8*(7^6*5^4-3)+2)+1$
158111478	$(-98+(7^6-5)^4\wedge 3)^*21$	169414451	$9^8*(7^6*5^4-3/2)-1$
158113359	$-9-(8-(7^6-5)^4\wedge 3)^*21$	169414453	$9^8*(7^6*5^4-3/2)+1$
158113377	$9-(8-(7^6-5)^4\wedge 3)^*21$	169414667	$9^8*(7^6*5^4+3/2)-1$
158113438	$-98+(7^6-5)^4\wedge 3^*21$	169414669	$9^8*(7^6*5^4+3/2)+1$
158113634	$98+(7^6-5)^4\wedge 3^*21$	169414757	$9*(8*(7^6*5^4+3)-2)-1$
158113695	$-9+(8+(7^6-5)^4\wedge 3)^*21$	169414759	$9*(8*(7^6*5^4+3)-2)+1$
158113713	$9+(8+(7^6-5)^4\wedge 3)^*21$	169414793	$9*(8*(7^6*5^4+3)+2)-1$
158115594	$(98+(7^6-5)^4\wedge 3)^*21$	169414795	$9*(8*(7^6*5^4+3)+2)+1$
158124918	$(-98+(7^6+5)^4\wedge 3)^*21$	169415631	$9*(-8+(7^6*5+4)^3\wedge 2-1)$
158126817	$9-(8-(7^6+5)^4\wedge 3)^*21$	169415649	$9*(-8+(7^6*5+4)^3\wedge 2+1)$
158126878	$-98+(7^6+5)^4\wedge 3^*21$	169415703	$9*((8+7^6*5-4)^3\wedge 2-1)$
158127074	$98+(7^6+5)^4\wedge 3^*21$	169415721	$9*((8+7^6*5-4)^3\wedge 2+1)$
158127135	$-9+(8+(7^6+5)^4\wedge 3)^*21$	169417449	$9*(8/7^6-6^5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$
158127153	$9+(8+(7^6+5)^4\wedge 3)^*21$	169418007	$9*((8+7^6*5+4)^3\wedge 2-1)$
158129034	$(98+(7^6+5)^4\wedge 3)^*21$	169418025	$9*((8+7^6*5+4)^3\wedge 2+1)$
158708403	$-98+7^6*(5+4^3)^*21$	169868673	$9+8*(76+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
158708599	$98+7^6*(5+4^3)^*21$	169869951	$-9+8*(76+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
159379913	$9-8*76*(5-4^3\wedge 2+1)$	169869969	$9+8*(76+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
159380511	$-9-8*(76*(5-4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	169921797	$9+8^7*((6-5+4)^3\wedge 2-1)$
159380513	$9-8*(76*(5-4^3\wedge 2)+1)$	169921971	$9+8^7*((6-5+4)^3\wedge 2+1)$
159380529	$9-8*(76*(5-4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	170355749	$(-9+8*7^6*543)/(2+1)$
159381129	$9-8*76*(5-4^3\wedge 2-1)$	170355755	$(9+8*7^6*543)/(2+1)$
159385993	$9+8*76*(5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	170471343	$(-98+7^6*(5+4^3))^*21$
159386575	$-9+8*(76*(5+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	170473224	$-9-(8-7^6*(5+4^3))^*21$
159386593	$9+8*(76*(5+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	170473242	$9-(8-7^6*(5+4^3))^*21$
159386609	$9+8*(76*(5+4^3\wedge 2)+1)$	170473303	$-98+7^6*(5+4^3)^*21$
159387191	$-9+8*76*(5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	170473499	$98+7^6*(5+4^3)^*21$
159387209	$9+8*76*(5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	170473560	$-9+(8+7^6*(5+4^3))^*21$
159432300	$9^8*(7-(6/(5+4)))^3\wedge 2-1$	170473578	$9+(8+7^6*(5+4^3))^*21$
160408458	$98*(7^6*5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	170475459	$(98+7^6*(5+4^3))^*21$
160429059	$9*((8-76)^*(5-4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	170695886	$9^8+7^6*(543^2-1)$
160429077	$9*((8-76)^*(5-4^3\wedge 2)+1)$	170826348	$9^8*7^6*(5^4+(3^2)\wedge-1)$
160435197	$-9*((8-76)^*(5+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	170931184	$9^8+7^6*(543^2+1)$
160693668	$9+(8*76+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	170938193	$(9/(8+((7^6+5^4)/3)^2))^{\wedge-1}$
160694894	$9+(8*76+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	171414495	$-98+7^6*(5+4)^3\wedge 2-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
171414521	$-9*8+7^6*((5+4)^3*2-1)$	177894927	$9*(8*7^6+54-3)*21$
171414665	$9*8+7^6*((5+4)^3*2-1)$	177896061	$9*(8*7^6+54+3)*21$
171414691	$98+7^6*((5+4)^3*2-1)$	177900975	$9*(8*(7^6+5)+43)*21$
171531837	$9*((-8+7^6*54)^3*2-1)$	177912504	$9*8*(7^6+54/3)*21$
171531981	$9*(-8+7^6*54^3*2-1)$	177915906	$9*(8/7^6-6+54^3)*21$
171532089	$9*(-8+(7^6*54-3)*(2+1))$	177925923	$9*(8/7^6-6+5^4*43)*21$
171532125	$9*(8+7^6*54^3*2-1)$	177942744	$9*8*(7^6-5+43)*21$
171532149	$9*(-8+7^6*54^3*2-1)$	177957864	$9*8*(7^6+5+43)*21$
171532161	$9*(-8+7^6*54^3*2+1)$	177962400	$9*8*(7^6+54-3)*21$
171532179	$9*(-8+7^6*54^3*2-1)$	177966369	$9*(8*(7^6+54)-3)*21$
171532191	$9*(-8+7^6*54^3)+21$	177967503	$9*(8*(7^6+54)+3)*21$
171532197	$9*(-8+7^6*54^3+2+1)$	177971472	$9*8*(7^6+54+3)*21$
171532293	$9*(8+7^6*54^3)-21$	179302320	$-9*(8+76*(5-4^3*2+1))$
171532335	$9*(8+7^6*54^3)+21$	179302995	$-9*(8+76*(5-4^3*2)+1)$
171532359	$9*(-8+7^6*54^3+21)$	179303013	$-9*(8+76*(5-4^3*2)-1)$
171532431	$9*((8+7^6*54)^3*2-1)$	179303157	$9*(8-76*(5-4^3*2)+1)$
171532485	$9*((8+7^6*54)^3+2+1)$	179303688	$-9*(8+76*(5-4^3*2-1))$
171532503	$9*(8+7^6*54^3+21)$	179309160	$-9*(8-76*(5+4^3*2-1))$
171532647	$9*((8+7^6*54)^3+21)$	179309835	$-9*(8-76*(5+4^3*2)+1)$
171649793	$-98+7^6*((5+4)^3*2+1)$	179309853	$-9*(8-76*(5+4^3*2)-1)$
171649819	$-9*8+7^6*((5+4)^3*2+1)$	179310528	$-9*(8-76*(5+4^3*2+1))$
171649963	$9*8+7^6*((5+4)^3*2+1)$	179310672	$9*(8+76*(5+4^3*2+1))$
171649989	$98+7^6*((5+4)^3*2+1)$	179358150	$(9^8-765)*(4+(3^2)^{\wedge}-1)$
172002821	$(9+8)*(7^6*(54+32)-1)$	179364525	$(9^8+765)*(4-(3^2)^{\wedge}-1)$
172002855	$(9+8)*(7^6*(54+32)+1)$	179785508	$-98*7*(65-4^3*2+1)$
172168572	$(9^8-7^6*54)*(3+2-1)$	179786096	$-98*(7*(65-4^3*2)+1)$
172170468	$(9^8-76*54)*(3+2-1)$	179786193	$98*7*(-65+4^3*2)-1$
172174644	$(9^8-765*4)*(3+2-1)$	179786195	$98*7*(-65+4^3*2)+1$
172185600	$9^8*(-7+6+5)-4*321$	179786292	$-98*(7*(65-4^3*2)-1)$
172185981	$9^8*(-7+6+5)-4*321$	179786880	$-98*7*(65-4^3*2-1)$
172186119	$(9^8-765/4)*(3+2-1)$	179810106	$-98*(7*(6^5-4^3*2)+1)$
172187649	$(9^8+765/4)*(3+2-1)$	179810302	$-98*(7*(6^5-4^3*2)-1)$
172187787	$9^8*(-7+6+5)+4*321$	179823336	$-98*(7*(6+5-4^3*2)-1)$
172188168	$9^8*(-7+6+5)+4*321$	179831372	$98*(7*(6-5+4^3*2)-1)$
172199124	$(9^8+765*4)*(3+2-1)$	179831568	$98*(7*(6-5+4^3*2)+1)$
172203300	$(9^8+76*54)*(3+2-1)$	179838232	$98*(7*(6+5+4^3*2)-1)$
172205196	$(9^8+7^6*54)*(3+2-1)$	179838428	$98*(7*(6+5+4^3*2)+1)$
172228023	$9*(8^7+65*(4^3*2-1))$	179874688	$98*7*(65+4^3*2-1)$
172229193	$9*(8^7+65*(4^3*2+1))$	179875276	$98*(7*(65+4^3*2)-1)$
172541178	$9^8*(7+6^6-5^4*3-2-1)$	179875373	$98*7*(65+4^3*2)-1$
172591011	$9*(-8+7^6*(54^3+2-1))$	179875375	$98*7*(65+4^3*2)+1$
172591155	$9*(8+7^6*(54^3+2-1))$	179875472	$98*(7*(65+4^3*2)+1)$
172931388	$98*(7^6*5-43)*(2+1)$	179876060	$98*7*(65+4^3*2+1)$
172942805	$98*((7^6*5-4)^3*2^{\wedge}-1)$	180701157	$(-9+8*(7^6-5)^4*43)*(2+1)$
172942903	$98*((7^6*5-4)^3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	180701211	$(9+8*(7^6-5)^4*43)*(2+1)$
172945157	$98*((7^6*5+4)^3*2^{\wedge}-1)$	180707877	$(-9+(8^7*6-5)/4^{\wedge}-3)*(2+1)$
172945255	$98*((7^6*5+4)^3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	180707931	$(9+(8^7*6-5)^4*43)*(2+1)$
172956672	$98*(7^6*5+43)*(2+1)$	180709797	$(-9+(8/7^6-6+5)/4^{\wedge}-3)*(2+1)$
173649843	$9*(-8+7^6*(54^3+2)-1)$	180709851	$(9+(8^7*6+5)^4*43)*(2+1)$
173649861	$9*(-8+7^6*(54^3+2)+1)$	180716517	$(-9+8*(7^6+5)^4*43)*(2+1)$
174496350	$98*(-7*(6^6-4^3*2)-1)$	180716571	$(9+8*(7^6+5)^4*43)*(2+1)$
174496546	$98*(-7*(6^6-4^3*2)+1)$	181061739	$9*(-8+7^6*(54+3)*(2+1))$
174707505	$9*(-8+(7^6*5-4)*(32+1))$	181061883	$9*(8+7^6*(54+3)*(2+1))$
174709881	$9*(-8+(7^6*5+4)*(32+1))$	181665099	$(-9*8+765)*(4^3*2-1)$
176160512	$(-9+8*7)*((6+5)^4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	181665719	$-9*(8-7*(6+5)^4*4^3*2)-1$
177799104	$9*8*(7^6-54-3)*21$	181665721	$-9*(8-7*(6+5)^4*4^3*2)+1$
177803073	$9*(8*(7^6-54)-3)*21$	181665863	$9*(8+7*(6+5)^4*4^3*2)-1$
177804207	$9*(8*(7^6-54)+3)*21$	181665865	$9*(8+7*(6+5)^4*4^3*2)+1$
177808176	$9*8*(7^6-54+3)*21$	181666485	$(-9*8+765)*(4^3*2+1)$
177812712	$9*8*(7^6-5-43)*21$	182112921	$9*(8*(7^6-5)^4*3/2+1)$
177827832	$9*8*(7^6+5-43)*21$	182452205	$9*(8^7*(6+5-4/3)-2)-1$
177844653	$9*(8/7^6-6-5^4*3)*21$	182452207	$9*(8^7*(6+5-4/3)-2)+1$
177854670	$9*(8/7^6-6-54^3)*21$	182452241	$9*(8^7*(6+5-4/3)+2)-1$
177858072	$9*8*(7^6-54/3)*21$	182452243	$9*(8^7*(6+5-4/3)+2)+1$
177869601	$9*(8*(7^6-5)-43)*21$	183872574	$9^8+7^6*(54+3)*21$
177874515	$9*(8*7^6-54-3)*21$	184319991	$-9-(8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}-4*(3-21)$
177875649	$9*(8*7^6-54+3)*21$	184320009	$9-(8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}-4*(3-21)$
177878106	$9*(8*7^6+5-43)*21$	185165022	$98*(7*(6^6+4^3*2)-1)$
177884793	$9+8*(7^6*(5+4)-3)*21$	185165218	$98*(7*(6^6+4^3*2)+1)$
177885234	$9*(8*7^6*(5+4)-3)*21$	186384375	$9*((8+76-5)^4*4^3*2-1)$
177885801	$9+8*(7^6*(5+4)+3)*21$	186384393	$9*((8+76-5)^4*4^3*2+1)$
177892470	$9*(8*7^6-5+43)*21$	186450841	$(9*8-7^6*5)*(4-321)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
186468276	$(9+8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4-321)$	191650437	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*543)*(2+1)$
186471120	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4-321)$	192935135	$(-9+8*7^{\wedge}6/5)*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
186471138	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4-321)$	192944361	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*(43-2)-1)$
186473348	$(9-8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4-321)$	192944377	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*(43-2)+1)$
186473593	$9*-8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-321)$	192953585	$(9+8*7^{\wedge}6/5)*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
186473648	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-321)$	193519792	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4*321)$
186473664	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-321)$	193637441	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*5*4^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
186473666	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-321)$	193709900	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)*(5+4)-3)/2-1$
186473682	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-321)$	193709902	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)*(5+4)-3)/2+1$
186473737	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-321)$	193709903	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)*(5+4)+3)/2-1$
186473982	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(-4+321)$	193709905	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)*(5+4)+3)/2+1$
186476192	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4-321)$	193710584	$((9^{\wedge}8+76)*(5+4)-3)/2-1$
186476210	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4-321)$	193710587	$((9^{\wedge}8+76)*(5+4)+3)/2-1$
186479054	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(-4+321)$	193710589	$((9^{\wedge}8+76)*(5+4)+3)/2+1$
186496489	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(-4+321)$	193767831	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54*3+21))$
187167229	$(-9-8)*(7*6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	193767975	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54*3+21))$
187167263	$(9+8)*(7*6*(-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	194101617	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4*321$
187174369	$(9+8)*(7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	194114457	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4*321$
187174403	$(9+8)*(7*6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	194696282	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4*321)$
188218674	$(9*87-65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	194826599	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)-2)-1$
188220110	$(9*87-65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	194826601	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)-2)+1$
188238310	$(-9+8/7^{\wedge}6-6*5*4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	194826725	$9*(8/(7^{\wedge}6-6/(5*4+3))-2)-1$
188238490	$(9+8/7^{\wedge}6-6*5*4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	194826727	$9*(8/(7^{\wedge}6-6/(5*4+3))-2)+1$
188825344	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*321$	194826761	$9*(8/(7^{\wedge}6-6/(5*4+3))+2)-1$
188825360	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*321$	194826763	$9*(8/(7^{\wedge}6-6/(5*4+3))+2)+1$
188825378	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*321$	194826887	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)+2)-1$
188827912	$-9-8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*321$	194826889	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)+2)+1$
188827928	$-9+8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*321$	195519825	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(3+21)$
188827930	$9-8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*321$	196001176	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-3)-21)$
188827946	$9+8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*321$	196003217	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3)*2-1)$
189035532	$(98*7^{\wedge}6-6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	196003251	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3)*2+1)$
189284428	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$	196005292	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-3)+21)$
189519726	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$	196082964	$(-9-8+765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
190238335	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43/2)+1)$	196084460	$(-9-8+765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
190238531	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43/2)-1)$	196942194	$(-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32-1)$
190696216	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$	196943899	$(-9-8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32-1)$
190931514	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$	196944169	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32-1)$
191041893	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7-65)^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	196944187	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32-1)$
191102175	$9*(-8+(76+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	196944354	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1)$
191103777	$9*(8+(76+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	196944395	$(-9+8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32-1)$
191106612	$9*((87-6)*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	196944409	$-9-8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1)$
191106630	$9*((87-6)*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	196944425	$-9+8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1)$
191156225	$(-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+321)$	196944427	$9-8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1)$
191174100	$(-9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+321)$	196944443	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1)$
191177016	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+321)$	196944457	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32-1)$
191177034	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+321)$	196944498	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1)$
191179300	$(-9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+321)$	196944665	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32-1)$
191179553	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321)$	196944683	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32-1)$
191179608	$-9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321)$	196944953	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32-1)$
191179624	$-9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321)$	196946658	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32-1)$
191179626	$9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321)$	198177093	$-9*((8+76)*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
191179642	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321)$	198184635	$9*((8+76)*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
191179697	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321)$	198184653	$9*((8+76)*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
191179950	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+321)$	198442242	$-9-(8-765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
191182216	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+321)$	198442260	$9-(8-765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
191182234	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+321)$	198442998	$-9-(8-765)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
191185150	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+321)$	198443000	$-9-(8-765)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
191203025	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+321)$	198443016	$9-(8-765)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
191405466	$98*(-7+(6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	198443018	$9-(8-765)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
191405662	$98*(-7+(6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	198443756	$-9-(8-765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
191650005	$(-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*543)*(2+1)$	198443774	$9-(8-765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
191650170	$(-9-8+7^{\wedge}6*543)*(2+1)$	199170135	$9*(87*(-6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
191650188	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*543)*(2+1)$	199170153	$9*(87*(-6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
191650197	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*543)/(2+1)$	200003283	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4*(3+2)-1)$
191650206	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*543)*(2+1)$	200003317	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4*(3+2)+1)$
191650218	$(-9+8+7^{\wedge}6*543)*(2+1)$	200120310	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)*21)$
191650224	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6*543)*(2+1)$	200121444	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)*21)$
191650236	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*543)*(2+1)$	200277252	$(-9+8+765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
191650245	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*543)/(2+1)$	200278780	$(-9+8+765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
191650254	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*543)*(2+1)$	200473897	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*43-2)-1)$
191650272	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6*543)*(2+1)$	200473913	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*43-2)+1)$
		200539323	$-9*8+765*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
200539378	$-9-8+765*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	203910948	$9*(87*6*((5^4/3)\wedge 2+1))$
200539394	$-9+8+765*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	204238665	$9+8*(7^6*(5^*43+2)-1)$
200539396	$9-8+765*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	204238681	$9+8*(7^6*(5^*43+2)+1)$
200539412	$9+8+765*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	204709269	$9+8*7^6*5*(43+2^{\wedge} -1)$
200539467	$9*8+765*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	205136226	$9\wedge 8*(7-(6/5/4^*3)\wedge -2-1)$
200540853	$-9*8+765*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	205207074	$-9*87*(65-4^3\wedge 2+1)$
200540908	$-9-8+765*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	205207848	$-9*(87*(65-4^3\wedge 2)+1)$
200540924	$-9+8+765*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	205207856	$-9*87*(65-4^3\wedge 2)-1$
200540926	$9-8+765*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	205207858	$-9*87*(65-4^3\wedge 2)+1$
200540942	$9+8+765*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	205207866	$-9*(87*(65-4^3\wedge 2)-1)$
200540997	$9*8+765*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	205208640	$-9*87*(65-4^3\wedge 2-1)$
200801538	$(9-8+765)*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	205235253	$-9*(87*(6*5-4^3\wedge 2)+1)$
200803070	$(9-8+765)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	205235271	$-9*(87*(6*5-4^3\wedge 2)-1)$
200881128	$(9\wedge 8-765)*(4+(3/2)\wedge -1)$	205250148	$-9*(87*(6+5-4^3\wedge 2)-1)$
200888268	$(9\wedge 8+765)*(4+(3/2)\wedge -1)$	205259526	$9*(87*(6-5+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$
201326403	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)*4/3-21)$	205259544	$9*(87*(6-5+4^3\wedge 2)+1)$
201326781	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)*4/3+21)$	205267356	$9*(87*(6+5+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$
201767963	$-9*8+7^6*5*(4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	205267374	$9*(87*(6+5+4^3\wedge 2)+1)$
201768107	$9*8+7^6*5*(4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	205308864	$9*87*(65+4^3\wedge 2-1)$
201768133	$98*(7^6*5*(4+3)/2+1)$	205309638	$9*(87*(65+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$
201770433	$9\wedge 8*(7^6\wedge -5*4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$	205309646	$9*87*(65+4^3\wedge 2)-1$
201885693	$9+8*7^6*(5*43-2^{\wedge} -1)$	205309648	$9*87*(65+4^3\wedge 2)+1$
202356285	$9+8*(7^6*5*43-2^{\wedge} -1)$	205309656	$9*(87*(65+4^3\wedge 2)+1)$
202356293	$9+8*(7^6*5*43+2^{\wedge} -1)$	205310430	$9*87*(65+4^3\wedge 2+1)$
202428369	$9*(87-6/5)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	205415082	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^*43-21))$
202636530	$-9+(8+765)*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	205415226	$9*(8+7^6*(5^*43-21))$
202636548	$9+(8+765)*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	205490520	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*((5-4^3)\wedge 2-1)$
202637302	$-9+(8+765)*4^3\wedge 2-1$	205608618	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*((5-4^3)\wedge 2+1)$
202637304	$-9+(8+765)*4^3\wedge 2+1$	207532150	$98*((7^6*(5+4)-3)^*2-1)$
202637320	$9+(8+765)*4^3\wedge 2-1$	207532346	$98*((7^6*(5+4)-3)^*2+1)$
202637322	$9+(8+765)*4^3\wedge 2+1$	207532542	$98*(7^6*54/3-2-1)$
202638076	$-9+(8+765)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	207532639	$98*(7^6*54/3-2)-1$
202638094	$9+(8+765)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	207532640	$98*(7^6*54/3-2)^{\wedge} 1$
202709129	$-98-7^6*(5-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	207532641	$98*(7^6*54/3-2)+1$
202709155	$9*-8-7^6*(5-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	207532738	$98*(7^6*54/3-2+1)$
202709299	$9*8-7^6*(5-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	207532787	$98*(7^6*54/3-2^{\wedge} -1)$
202709325	$98-7^6*(5-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	207532885	$98*(7^6*54/3+2^{\wedge} -1)$
203179751	$-9*8+7^6*(54*32-1)$	207532934	$98*(7^6*54/3+2-1)$
203179806	$-9-8+7^6*(54*32-1)$	207533031	$98*(7^6*54/3+2)-1$
203179822	$-9+8+7^6*(54*32-1)$	207533032	$98*(7^6*54/3+2)^{\wedge} 1$
203179824	$9-8+7^6*(54*32-1)$	207533033	$98*(7^6*54/3+2)+1$
203179840	$9+8+7^6*(54*32-1)$	207533130	$98*(7^6*54/3+2+1)$
203179895	$9*8+7^6*(54*32-1)$	207533326	$98*((7^6*(5+4)+3)^*2-1)$
203204160	$9*8*(7^6-54)*(3+21)$	207533522	$98*((7^6*(5+4)+3)^*2+1)$
203285808	$9*(8*7^6-54)*(3+21)$	208084959	$9\wedge 8*7-654^3/(2+1)$
203288734	$-98+(7^6-5)*(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	208090701	$9*((87+6/5)*(4^3\wedge 2+1))$
203288930	$98+(7^6-5)*(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	209453039	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
203306014	$-98+(7^6+5)*(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	209453073	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
203306210	$98+(7^6+5)*(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	209648142	$(-9*8+7^6*54)*(32+1)$
203309136	$9*(8*7^6+54)*(3+21)$	209649957	$(-9-8+7^6*54)*(32+1)$
203390784	$9*8*(7^6+54)*(3+21)$	209650245	$-9-(8-7^6*54)*(32+1)$
203415049	$-9*8+7^6*(54*32+1)$	209650263	$9-(8-7^6*54)*(32+1)$
203415104	$-9-8+7^6*(54*32+1)$	209650446	$-9*8+7^6*54*(32+1)$
203415120	$-9+8+7^6*(54*32+1)$	209650485	$(-9+8+7^6*54)*(32+1)$
203415122	$9-8+7^6*(54*32+1)$	209650501	$-9-8+7^6*54*(32+1)$
203415138	$9+8+7^6*(54*32+1)$	209650517	$-9+8+7^6*54*(32+1)$
203415193	$9*8+7^6*(54*32+1)$	209650519	$9-8+7^6*54*(32+1)$
203885619	$-98+7^6*(5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	209650535	$9+8+7^6*54*(32+1)$
203885645	$-9*8+7^6*(5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	209650551	$(9-8+7^6*54)*(32+1)$
203885789	$9*8+7^6*(5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	209650590	$9*8+7^6*54*(32+1)$
203885815	$98+7^6*(5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	209650773	$-9+(8+7^6*54)*(32+1)$
203901552	$9*87*6*((5^4/3)\wedge 2-1)$	209650791	$9+(8+7^6*54)*(32+1)$
203905467	$9*87*(6*(5^4/3)\wedge 2-1)$	209651079	$(9+8+7^6*54)*(32+1)$
203905719	$-9+87*6*(5^4\wedge(3/2)-1)$	209652894	$(9*8+7^6*54)*(32+1)$
203905737	$9+87*6*(5^4\wedge(3/2)-1)$	209988114	$(9+8)*(7^6*5-43)^*21$
203906154	$-9+87*(6*5^4\wedge(3/2)-1)$	210018816	$(9+8)*(7^6*5+43)^*21$
203906172	$9+87*(6*5^4\wedge(3/2)-1)$	210659722	$98*((7+6/5)*(4^3\wedge 2+1))$
203906328	$-9+87*(6*5^4\wedge(3/2)+1)$	211347351	$9*(87*(6^{\wedge} 5+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$
203906346	$9+87*(6*5^4\wedge(3/2)+1)$	211347369	$9*(87*(6^{\wedge} 5+4^3\wedge 2)+1)$
203906763	$-9+87*6*(5^4\wedge(3/2)+1)$	213297539	$98*(7^6*(5^*4-3/2)-1)$
203906781	$9+87*6*(5^4\wedge(3/2)+1)$	213297735	$98*(7^6*(5^*4-3/2)+1)$
203907033	$9*(87*(6*(5^4/3)\wedge 2+1))$	214461314	$9\wedge 8+7^6*((5+4)^3*2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
214696612	$9^8 + 7^8 * ((5+4)^3 * 2 + 1)$	227647530	$9 * ((-8 + 7^8 * 5)^4 * 3 - 21)$
216414585	$9^8 * (((7+6)/(5+4))^3 * 2 - 1)$	227647908	$9 * ((-8 + 7^8 * 5)^4 * 3 + 21)$
216474169	$9 + 8 * 7^8 * 5 * (43 + 2 + 1)$	227650554	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5^4 * 3 - 21)$
217062324	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5 * (43 - 2) - 1)$	227650698	$9 * (8 + 7^8 * 5^4 * 3 - 21)$
217062342	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5 * (43 - 2) + 1)$	227650716	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5^4 * 3 - 2 - 1)$
217065348	$9 * ((8 + 7^8 * 5) * (43 - 2) - 1)$	227650722	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5^4 * 3) - 21$
217065366	$9 * ((8 + 7^8 * 5) * (43 - 2) + 1)$	227650734	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5^4 * 3 - 2 + 1)$
218454271	$(9 - 8^8) / 6 / 5^4 - 4 + (3 * 2)^4 - 1$	227650752	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5^4 * 3 + 2 - 1)$
219410352	$-9 * ((87 + 6) * (5 - 4^3 * 2) - 1)$	227650764	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5^4 * 3) + 21$
219413691	$(9 * 8 + 765) * (4^3 * 2 - 1)$	227650770	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5^4 * 3 + 2 + 1)$
219415365	$(9 * 8 + 765) * (4^3 * 2 + 1)$	227650866	$9 * (8 + 7^8 * 5^4 * 3) - 21$
219418704	$9 * ((87 + 6) * (5 + 4^3 * 2) - 1)$	227650908	$9 * (8 + 7^8 * 5^4 * 3) + 21$
219418722	$9 * ((87 + 6) * (5 + 4^3 * 2) + 1)$	227650932	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5^4 * 3 + 21)$
219532936	$-98 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3) * (2 + 1)$	227651076	$9 * (8 + 7^8 * 5^4 * 3 + 21)$
219533132	$98 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3) * (2 + 1)$	227653722	$9 * ((8 + 7^8 * 5) * 43 - 21)$
220069070	$9 * (-8 + 7 * (6 - 5^4 * 3)^2) - 1$	227653884	$9 * ((8 + 7^8 * 5) * 43 - 2 - 1)$
220069072	$9 * (-8 + 7 * (6 - 5^4 * 3)^2) + 1$	227653902	$9 * ((8 + 7^8 * 5) * 43 - 2 + 1)$
220069214	$9 * (8 + 7 * (6 - 5^4 * 3)^2) - 1$	227653920	$9 * ((8 + 7^8 * 5) * 43 + 2 - 1)$
220069216	$9 * (8 + 7 * (6 - 5^4 * 3)^2) + 1$	227653938	$9 * ((8 + 7^8 * 5) * 43 + 2 + 1)$
220238830	$-98 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 - 2 - 1)$	227654100	$9 * ((8 + 7^8 * 5) * 43 + 21)$
220239026	$98 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 - 2 - 1)$	228326544	$-9 + (876 - 5) * (4^3 * 2 - 1)$
220474128	$-98 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 - 2 + 1)$	228326562	$9 + (876 - 5) * (4^3 * 2 - 1)$
220474154	$-9 * 8 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 - 2 + 1)$	228327414	$-9 + (876 - 5) * 4^3 * 2 - 1$
220474298	$9 * 8 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 - 2 + 1)$	228327416	$-9 + (876 - 5) * 4^3 * 2 + 1$
220474324	$98 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 - 2 + 1)$	228327432	$9 + (876 - 5) * 4^3 * 2 - 1$
220576686	$9 * ((-8 + 7^8) * 5^4 / 3 - 21)$	228327434	$9 + (876 - 5) * 4^3 * 2 + 1$
220577064	$9 * ((-8 + 7^8) * 5^4 / 3 + 21)$	228328286	$-9 + (876 - 5) * (4^3 * 2 + 1)$
220606686	$9 * ((8 + 7^8) * 5^4 / 3 - 21)$	228328304	$9 + (876 - 5) * (4^3 * 2 + 1)$
220607064	$9 * ((8 + 7^8) * 5^4 / 3 + 21)$	228588696	$(-9 + 876 + 5) * (4^3 * 2 - 1)$
220607793	$(9^8 + (7 - 65^4) * 3) * 2 - 21$	228590440	$(-9 + 876 + 5) * (4^3 * 2 + 1)$
220608675	$(9^8 - (7 + 65^4) * 3) * 2 - 21$	228709773	$9 * (8 * (7^8 * 5^4 + 3) / 2 + 1)$
220709426	$-98 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 + 2 - 1)$	228944954	$98 * 7^8 * 5 * (5^4 - 3 / 21)$
220709452	$-9 * 8 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 + 2 - 1)$	229520386	$9^8 - 7^8 * 5 * (4 - 321)$
220709596	$9 * 8 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 + 2 - 1)$	229632879	$-9 - 876 * (5 - 4^3 * 2 + 1)$
220709622	$98 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 + 2 - 1)$	229632897	$9 - 876 * (5 - 4^3 * 2 + 1)$
220944724	$-98 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 + 2 + 1)$	229633754	$-9 - 876 * (5 - 4^3 * 2) - 1$
220944750	$-9 * 8 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 + 2 + 1)$	229633756	$-9 - 876 * (5 - 4^3 * 2) + 1$
220944894	$9 * 8 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 + 2 + 1)$	229633772	$9 - 876 * (5 - 4^3 * 2) - 1$
220944920	$98 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 + 2 + 1)$	229633774	$9 - 876 * (5 - 4^3 * 2) + 1$
221374701	$9^8 - (8 + 7 + 6) * (5^4 * 3 * 2 - 1)$	229634631	$-9 - 876 * (5 - 4^3 * 2 - 1)$
221492799	$9^8 - (8 + 7 + 6) * (5^4 * 3 * 2 + 1)$	229634649	$9 - 876 * (5 - 4^3 * 2 - 1)$
2216500618	$-98 + 7^8 * (5^4 + 3) * (2 + 1)$	229641639	$-9 + 876 * (5 + 4^3 * 2 - 1)$
221650814	$98 + 7^8 * (5^4 + 3) * (2 + 1)$	229641657	$9 + 876 * (5 + 4^3 * 2 - 1)$
222297264	$(9 * 87 + 65) * (4^3 * 2 - 1)$	229642514	$-9 + 876 * (5 + 4^3 * 2) - 1$
222298960	$(9 * 87 + 65) * (4^3 * 2 + 1)$	229642516	$-9 + 876 * (5 + 4^3 * 2) + 1$
222356538	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5 * (43 - 2 + 1))$	229642532	$9 + 876 * (5 + 4^3 * 2) - 1$
222356610	$98 * 7^8 * 5 * (4 - 3 / 21)$	229642534	$9 + 876 * (5 + 4^3 * 2) + 1$
222876696	$(-98 + 7^8) * (5^4 * 3 + 21)$	229643391	$-9 + 876 * (5 + 4^3 * 2 + 1)$
222904070	$-9 * (8 - 7 * (6 + 5^4 * 3)^2) - 1$	229643409	$9 + 876 * (5 + 4^3 * 2 + 1)$
222904072	$-9 * (8 - 7 * (6 + 5^4 * 3)^2) + 1$	229686226	$-98 * (7 - 6 * (5^4 * 4^3 / 2) - 1)$
222904214	$9 * (8 + 7 * (6 + 5^4 * 3)^2) - 1$	229686716	$-98 * (7 - 6 * 5^4 * 4^3 / 2 + 1)$
222904216	$9 * (8 + 7 * (6 + 5^4 * 3)^2) + 1$	229686912	$-98 * (7 - 6 * 5^4 * 4^3 / 2 - 1)$
222985091	$9 * 8 * (7 / (6 + 5^4) * 3 * 21)$	229687402	$-98 * (7 - 6 * (5^4 * 4^3 / 2) + 1)$
223047327	$-9 - (8 - 7^8) * (5^4 * 3 + 21)$	229687598	$98 * (7 + 6 * (5^4 * 4^3 / 2) - 1)$
223047345	$9 - (8 - 7^8) * (5^4 * 3 + 21)$	229688088	$98 * (7 + 6 * 5^4 * 4^3 / 2 - 1)$
223062406	$-98 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 + 21)$	229688284	$98 * (7 + 6 * 5^4 * 4^3 / 2 + 1)$
223062602	$98 + 7^8 * (5^4 * 3 + 21)$	229688774	$98 * (7 + 6 * (5^4 * 4^3 / 2) + 1)$
223077663	$-9 + (8 + 7^8) * (5^4 * 3 + 21)$	229768416	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5 * (5^4 * 3 + 2) - 1)$
223077681	$9 + (8 + 7^8) * (5^4 * 3 + 21)$	229768434	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5 * (5^4 * 3 + 2) + 1)$
223248312	$(98 + 7^8) * (5^4 * 3 + 21)$	230582142	$98 * ((7^8 - 5) * 4 * (3 + 2) - 1)$
225533052	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5 * (5^4 * 3 - 2) - 1)$	230582338	$98 * ((7^8 - 5) * 4 * (3 + 2) + 1)$
225533070	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5 * (5^4 * 3 - 2) + 1)$	230588806	$98 * (7^8 * 5 * 4 - 32 - 1)$
225885648	$(-9 + 8 * 7^8 * 5) * ((4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	230589002	$98 * (7^8 * 5 * 4 - 32 + 1)$
225886512	$(9 + 8 * 7^8 * 5) * ((4 + 3)^2 - 1)$	230589394	$98 * (7^8 * 5 * 4 - 3^3 * (2 + 1))$
225967266	$(-9 + 876 - 5) * (4^3 * 2 - 1)$	230591060	$98 * (7^8 * 5 * 4 - 3^3 * 2 - 1)$
225968990	$(-9 + 876 - 5) * (4^3 * 2 + 1)$	230591256	$98 * (7^8 * 5 * 4 - 3^3 * 2 + 1)$
226591902	$9 * (-8 + 7^8 * 5 * (5^4 * 3 - 2 + 1))$	230591697	$98 * (7^8 * 5 * 4 - 3 - 2^2 - 1)$
226592046	$9 * (8 + 7^8 * 5 * (5^4 * 3 - 2 + 1))$	230591795	$98 * (7^8 * 5 * 4 - 3 / 2 - 1)$
227273646	$(9 - 876) * (5 - 4^3 * 2 + 1)$	230591991	$98 * (7^8 * 5 * 4 - 3 / 2 + 1)$
227275380	$(9 - 876) * (5 - 4^3 * 2 - 1)$	230592026	$98 * (7^8 * 5 * 4 - 3 / 21)$
227282316	$(-9 + 876) * (5 + 4^3 * 2 - 1)$	230592054	$98 * (7^8 * 5 * 4 + 3 / 21)$
227284050	$(-9 + 876) * (5 + 4^3 * 2 + 1)$	230592089	$98 * (7^8 * 5 * 4 + 3 / 2 - 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
230592285	$98^*(7^6*5^4+3/2+1)$	239197059	$9-(8+7)^6*(5^4-4/3-21)$
230592383	$98^*(7^6*5^4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	239198741	$-9+((8+7)^6-5^4/3)*21$
230592824	$98^*(7^6*5^4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	239198759	$9+((8+7)^6-5^4/3)*21$
230593020	$98^*(7^6*5^4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	239207491	$-9+((8+7)^6+5^4/3)*21$
230594686	$98^*(7^6*5^4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	239207509	$9+((8+7)^6+5^4/3)*21$
230595078	$98^*(7^6*5^4+32-1)$	239209191	$-9+(8+7)^6*(5^4-4/3+21)$
230595274	$98^*(7^6*5^4+32+1)$	239209209	$9+(8+7)^6*(5^4-4/3+21)$
230601742	$98^*((7^6+5)^4*(3+2)-1)$	239242491	$-9+((8+7)^6+5^4*3)*21$
230601938	$98^*((7^6+5)^4*(3+2)+1)$	239242509	$9+((8+7)^6+5^4*3)*21$
230685840	$98^*(876-5)^*(4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$	239257791	$-9+(8+7)^6*(5^4-4^3+21)$
230687600	$(9+876-5)^*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$	239257809	$9+(8+7)^6*(5^4-4^3+21)$
230827266	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4+3+2+1))$	239297994	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4+3+2+1))$
230827410	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4+3+2+1))$	239298138	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4+3+2+1))$
230947974	$-9+(876+5)^*(4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$	239991147	$9^8+7^6*5^4*(32-1)$
230947992	$9+(876+5)^*(4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$	240003943	$(9+8)^*(7^6*5^4*3^2-1)$
230948854	$-9+(876+5)^*4^3^{\wedge}2-1$	240003977	$(9+8)^*(7^6*5^4*3^2+1)$
230948856	$-9+(876+5)^*4^3^{\wedge}2+1$	240983514	$9*((8+7+65^4*3)/2+1)$
230948872	$9+(876+5)^*4^3^{\wedge}2-1$	241415757	$9*(8^7*7^6*(5+4^3)/2+1)$
230948874	$9+(876+5)^*4^3^{\wedge}2+1$	241692892	$98^*(7^6-5^4/3)*21$
230949736	$-9+(876+5)^*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$	241886353	$9+8/7^6*(5+4^3*21)$
230949754	$9+(876+5)^*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$	242550392	$98^*(7^6+5^4/3)*21$
231292272	$9^8+(7+6)^{\wedge}(-5+4^3)* (2+1)$	243533358	$9*(-8+7^6*5^4*(43+2+1))$
231992130	$(-9-876)^*(5-4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$	243586116	$9^8+765*(4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$
231993900	$(-9-876)^*(5-4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$	243587646	$9^8+765*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$
232000980	$(9+876)^*(5+4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$	244814756	$9^8+7^6*5^4*(4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
232002750	$(9+876)^*(5+4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$	245755948	$9^8-7^6*(5-(4^3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
232239126	$98^*7^6*(5^4+3/21)$	245980392	$98^*(7^6+5^4*3)*21$
232421858	$(9+8)^*(7*(6-5+4)^3^{\wedge}2-1)$	246004042	$(-9-8)^*(7^6*(5-4^3*2)+1)$
232421892	$(9+8)^*(7*(6-5+4)^3^{\wedge}2+1)$	246004076	$(-9-8)^*(7^6*(5-4^3*2)-1)$
232783853	$9*(8^7*(6+5+4/3)-2)-1$	246226544	$9^8+7^6*(54^3*32-1)$
232783855	$9*(8^7*(6+5+4/3)-2)+1$	246335553	$9^8+(7^6-5)^*(4^3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
232783889	$9*(8^7*(6+5+4/3)+2)-1$	246352833	$9^8+(7^6+5)^*(4^3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
232783891	$9*(8^7*(6+5+4/3)+2)+1$	246461842	$9^8+7^6*(54^3*32+1)$
233307270	$(9+876+5)^*(4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$	246932438	$9^8+7^6*(5+(4^3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
233309050	$(9+876+5)^*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$	247875810	$98^*((7^6-5)^4/32-1)$
233886212	$-98^*7^6*(5/(4+3)-21)$	247876006	$98^*((7^6-5)^4/32+1)$
234226346	$9^8+7^6*5^4*(4+321)$	247886345	$98^*(7^6*(5^4+3/2)-1)$
234365460	$9^8*(76/(5+4)-3)-21$	247886541	$98^*(7^6*(5^4+3/2)+1)$
234365502	$9^8*(76/(5+4)-3)+21$	247896880	$98^*((7^6+5)^4/32-1)$
234696942	$9^8+7^6*5^4*(2+1)$	247897076	$98^*((7^6+5)^4/32+1)$
234896922	$9^8*((7-6/(5+4))/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	250870860	$9+8^7*(6+5)^*(4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$
235297550	$(-9+8^7*7^6*5^4*(4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	250871712	$-9+8^7*((6+5)^4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
235298450	$(9+8^7*7^6*5^4*(4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	250871730	$9+8^7*((6+5)^4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
235605510	$9^8*(7-6^{\wedge}-5^4*(3^2)-1)$	250871904	$9+8^7*((6+5)^4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
236003877	$(-9-8)^*(7^6*(5-4^3)*2+1)$	250872756	$-9+8^7*(6+5)^*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$
236003911	$(-9-8)^*(7^6*(5-4^3)*2-1)$	250872774	$9+8^7*(6+5)^*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$
236346796	$98^*(7^6-5)^*(43/2-1)$	252042328	$9^8*-7+65^4*(32-1)$
236366886	$98^*(7^6+5)^*(43/2-1)$	252611622	$9^8*(7-6^{\wedge}-5^4*(3+2)-1)$
236715843	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)^4*3)*21$	252697239	$9^8+7^6*5^4*(32+1)$
236716221	$(9+8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)^4*3)*21$	253180657	$9+8^7*7^6*(54^3*(3+2)-1)$
236727441	$9^8*((7+6-(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)/2-1)$	253502563	$(-9^8+7^6*5^4*(432-1))$
236786490	$9^8*((7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)/2-1)$	253526268	$(-9-8+7^6*5^4*(432-1))$
237180393	$9+8^7*7^6*(5+4+3)*21$	253530138	$-9-(8-7^6*5^4*(432-1))$
237499383	$-9+8^7*7^6*(5^4*(3/2)-1)$	253530156	$9-(8-7^6*5^4*(432-1))$
237499401	$9+8^7*7^6*(5^4*(3/2)-1)$	253533164	$(-9+8+7^6*5^4*(432-1))$
237499983	$-9+8^7*(76*5^4*(3/2)-1)$	253533523	$-9^8+7^6*5^4*(432-1)$
237499999	$-9+8^7*(76*5^4*(3/2)+1)$	253533578	$-9-8+7^6*5^4*(432-1)$
237500001	$9+8^7*(76*5^4*(3/2)-1)$	253533594	$-9+8+7^6*5^4*(432-1)$
237500017	$9+8^7*(76*5^4*(3/2)+1)$	253533596	$9-8+7^6*5^4*(432-1)$
237500599	$-9+8^7*7^6*(5^4*(3/2)+1)$	253533612	$9+8+7^6*5^4*(432-1)$
237500617	$9+8^7*7^6*(5^4*(3/2)+1)$	253533667	$9^8+7^6*5^4*(432-1)$
238242456	$9*((8+7^6*5^4*(43+2)-1)$	253534026	$(9-8+7^6*5^4*(432-1))$
238242474	$9*((8+7^6*5^4*(43+2)+1)$	253537034	$-9+(8+7^6*5^4*(432-1))$
238262892	$98^*(7^6-5^4*3)*21$	253537052	$9+(8+7^6*5^4*(432-1))$
238550130	$98/7^6*(4^3^{\wedge}2-1)$	253540922	$(9+8+7^6*5^4*(432-1))$
238551026	$98/7^6*(65^4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	253564627	$(9^8+7^6*5^4*(432-1))$
238551054	$98/7^6*(65^4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	253852837	$9^8*((7/6+54)^3*21)$
238551950	$98/7^6*(4^3^{\wedge}2+1)$	254004174	$-9-8+7^6*(5^4*432-1)$
238827470	$98^*7^6*(5^4*(4+3/21))$	254004190	$-9+8+7^6*(5^4*432-1)$
239163741	$-9+((8+7)^6-5^4*3)*21$	254004192	$9-8+7^6*(5^4*432-1)$
239163759	$9+((8+7)^6-5^4*3)*21$	254004208	$9+8+7^6*(5^4*432-1)$
239197041	$-9-(8+7)^6*(5^4-4/3-21)$	254239472	$-9-8+7^6*(5^4*432+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
254239488	$-9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*432+1)$	265180748	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)-2+1)$
254239490	$9-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*432+1)$	265180797	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$
254239506	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*432+1)$	265180895	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$
254501190	$9^{\wedge}8*(7-(6/(5+4)))^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	265180944	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)+2-1)$
254592427	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(543/2-1)$	265181140	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)+2+1)$
254592445	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(543/2-1)$	265182904	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)+21)$
254678909	$(-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	266251941	$9^{\wedge}8*(7/((6/5/-4+3)/2)+1)$
254702724	$(-9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	266827860	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4+3)*21)$
254706612	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	267186744	$-9*(8-76*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1))$
254706630	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	267186888	$9*(8+76*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1))$
254709652	$(-9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	267187419	$-9*(8-76*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
254710013	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(432+1)$	267187437	$-9*(8-76*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
254710068	$-9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(432+1)$	267187563	$9*(8+76*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
254710084	$-9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(432+1)$	267187581	$9*(8+76*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
254710086	$9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(432+1)$	267188112	$-9*(8-76*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1))$
254710102	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(432+1)$	267188256	$9*(8+76*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1))$
254710157	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(432+1)$	267964536	$98*(7*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1)$
254710518	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	267964732	$98*(7*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))+1)$
254713540	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	267972768	$98*(7*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1)$
254713558	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	267972964	$98*(7*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))+1)$
254717446	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	268435420	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)*4)*(3+2-1)$
254741261	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	268435492	$(9+8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)*4)*(3+2-1)$
254802753	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1))$	270122113	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)*32-1$
254805183	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1))$	270883287	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}-6-5^{\wedge}4)*32-1$
255393783	$9*(8^{\wedge}7*(-6+5^{\wedge}4/32)-1)$	270883305	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}-6-5^{\wedge}4)*32+1$
255393801	$9*(8^{\wedge}7*(-6+5^{\wedge}4/32)+1)$	270938808	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32-1)$
255533611	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*543/2-1)$	270938871	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32-1)$
255533627	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*543/2+1)$	270938889	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32+1)$
255533629	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*543/2-1)$	270938952	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32+1)$
255533645	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*543/2+1)$	271042551	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32-1)$
255589434	$9+(8+7)*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	271042569	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32+1)$
255590376	$-9+(8+7)*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	271047735	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32-1)$
255590394	$9+(8+7)*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	271047753	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32+1)$
255590424	$9+(8+7)*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	271050615	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4)*32-1$
255591366	$-9+(8+7)*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	271050633	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4)*32+1$
255591384	$9+(8+7)*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	271052919	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4)*32-1$
255993327	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	271052937	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4)*32+1$
255993361	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	271060407	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32-1)$
256015087	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	271060425	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32+1)$
256015121	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	271060983	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*32-1)$
256474811	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(543/2+1)$	271061001	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*32+1)$
256474829	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(543/2+1)$	271062945	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32+1)$
257160582	$9^{\wedge}8*(7-(6/(5+4)))^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	271065591	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*32-1)$
258279423	$9^{\wedge}8*(7-6+5)-43*21$	271065609	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*32+1)$
258281229	$9^{\wedge}8*(7-6+5)+43*21$	271066167	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32-1)$
259400070	$9^{\wedge}8*(7+(6/(5+4)))^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	271066185	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32+1)$
259405020	$98*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43/2+1)$	271073655	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)-4)*32-1$
259427070	$98*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43/2+1)$	271073673	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)-4)*32+1$
260474895	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(5/4-32)-1)$	271075959	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4)*32-1$
261060313	$(9+8)/((7/((6^{\wedge}5*4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)))$	271075977	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4)*32+1$
262059462	$9^{\wedge}8*(7+(6/(5+4)))^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	271078839	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32-1)$
262472040	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32-1$	271078857	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32+1)$
262577502	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32-1$	271084023	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*32-1)$
262579755	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)*(2+1)$	271084041	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*32+1)$
262607634	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32-1$	271187640	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32-1)$
262713096	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32-1$	271187703	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32-1)$
263285649	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2-1)$	271187721	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32+1)$
263520947	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2+1)$	271187784	$9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32+1)$
263756245	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2-1)$	271243287	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32-1)$
263949030	$9+8*(7+6^{\wedge}-5*4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$	271243305	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32+1)$
263991543	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1)$	272503287	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32-1)$
264201768	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7*6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	272503305	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32+1)$
264201786	$9+(8^{\wedge}7*6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	272628912	$9^{\wedge}8*(7-6/(5+4))-321$
264236768	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7*6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	272629554	$9^{\wedge}8*(7-6/(5+4))+321$
264236786	$9+(8^{\wedge}7*6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	275498879	$((9^{\wedge}8-7+6)/5-4)*32-1$
264245518	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7*6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	275499135	$((9^{\wedge}8-7+6)/5+4)*32-1$
264245536	$9+(8^{\wedge}7*6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	275499137	$((9^{\wedge}8-7+6)/5+4)*32+1$
264280518	$-9+(8^{\wedge}7*6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	276004537	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)*2-1)$
264280536	$9+(8^{\wedge}7*6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	276004571	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)*2+1)$
264697437	$9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)*(2+1)$	276037623	$9*(87+6*5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
265178788	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)-21)$	276037641	$9*(87+6*5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
265180552	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)-2-1)$	276251839	$((9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6)/5-4)*32-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
276251841	$((9^8+7^6)/5-4)*32+1$	298359440	$-9-(8*7^6+5)*(4-32)$
276252095	$((9^8+7^6)/5+4)*32-1$	298359458	$9-(8*7^6+5)*(4-32)$
276252097	$((9^8+7^6)/5+4)*32+1$	298370535	$-9-8*(7^6+5)*(4-32)$
276479757	$(-9+(8^7/(-6)/5)^{-4})/3^{(-2-1)}$	298370553	$9-8*(7^6+5)*(4-32)$
276480243	$(9+(8^7/(-6)/5)^{-4})*3^{(2+1)}$	298799847	$9^8*7-6^5*(4+32)$
276710350	$98*(7^6*(5+43)/2-1)$	298862055	$9^8*7+6^5*(4-32)$
276710546	$98*(7^6*(5+43)/2+1)$	299428407	$9*((8-76^(-5+4+3))^{2-1})$
277651649	$9-8/7^6-5*(4-3*21)$	299428425	$9*((8-76^(-5+4+3))^{2+1})$
278004570	$(9+8)*(7^6*(-5+(4*3)^2)-1)$	299557947	$9^8*7-6*(543^2+1)$
278004604	$(9+8)*(7^6*(-5+(4*3)^2)+1)$	299557959	$9^8*7-6*(543^2-1)$
278906233	$(9+8)*(7^6*5^4*(3/2)-1)$	300382137	$9^8*7-6*(54^3+21)$
278906267	$(9+8)*(7^6*5^4*(3/2)+1)$	300382389	$9^8*7-6*(54^3-21)$
279405720	$9*8*(7^6-54)*(32+1)$	300517623	$-9+8*(7^6-5^4)*32$
279517986	$9*(8*7^6-54)*(32+1)$	300517641	$9+8*(7^6-5^4)*32$
279550062	$9*(8*7^6+54)*(32+1)$	300703023	$9^8*7-6^5/4*32$
279662328	$9*8*(7^6+54)*(32+1)$	300946133	$-9-8*7^6*(5/4-32)$
280955142	$9^8*(7+6^5-5^4*(3^2)-1)$	300946151	$9-8*7^6*(5/4+32)$
281191338	$9^8*(7+6^5)*(5+4^3)^2+1$	301091895	$9*((8+76^(-5+4+3))^{2-1})$
281416399	$-9+8*7^6*(5^4*3-21)$	301091913	$9*((8+76^(-5+4+3))^{2+1})$
281416417	$9+8*7^6*(5^4*3-21)$	301124496	$9^8*7-(6+5^4)*32$
282589468	$98*(-7+(6+5)*(4^3*2-1))$	301128348	$9^8*7+(6-5^4)*32$
282590448	$98*(-7+(6+5)*4^3*2-1)$	301162848	$9^8*7-(6^5+4^3)*21$
282590644	$98*(-7+(6+5)*4^3*2+1)$	301164654	$9^8*7-(6^5-4^3)*21$
282591624	$98*(-7+(6+5)*(4^3*2+1))$	301181263	$-9+8*(7^6*5^4*3-21)$
282592996	$98*(7+(6+5)*(4^3*2+1))$	301181281	$9+8*(7^6*5^4*3-21)$
283056849	$9^8*((76/54)^3*2+1)$	301181617	$9+8*(7^6*5^4*3+21)$
284828157	$9*(-8+7^6*(54*(3+2)-1))$	301206797	$9^8*7-6^5*(4^3*2+1)$
284828301	$9*(8+7^6*(54*(3+2)-1))$	301206927	$9^8*7-6^5*(4^3*2-1)$
285886989	$9*(-8+7^6*54*(3+2)-1)$	301239687	$9^8*7-6^5*4^3*21$
285887007	$9*(-8+7^6*54*(3+2)+1)$	301267977	$9^8*(7-(6/54)^3)-21$
285887421	$9*((8+7^6*54)*(3+2)-1)$	301268019	$9^8*(7-(6/54)^3)+21$
285887439	$9*((8+7^6*54)*(3+2)+1)$	301309713	$9^8*7-6*(5+4)*32$
286122359	$-9+8*7^6*(5^4-32)$	301311738	$9^8*7-(6/54)^3-3*21$
286122377	$9+8*7^6*(5^4-32)$	301312923	$9^8*7-(6+5)*4*32$
286945839	$9*(-8+7^6*(54*(3+2)+1))$	301314057	$9^8*7-6^5*(4^3+1)$
286945983	$9*(8+7^6*(54*(3+2)+1))$	301314081	$9^8*7-6*(5^4*3+1)$
287063011	$(-9+8*7^6*5)*(4^3-2-1)$	301314093	$9^8*7-6*(5^4*3-1)$
287064109	$(9+8*7^6*5)*(4^3-2-1)$	301314117	$9^8*7-6^5*(4^3-2-1)$
287743578	$9^8*-7+6^5*4*(3+1)$	301316133	$9^8*7-(6^5+4)*32$
287992495	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)*(4^3)^2-1)$	301316673	$9^8*7-6*(5^4*3+1)$
287992529	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)*(4^3)^2+1)$	301316685	$9^8*7-6*(5^4*3-1)$
288016975	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*(4^3)^2-1)$	301317114	$9^8*7-(6+5)*4^3*21$
288017009	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)*(4^3)^2+1)$	301317273	$9^8*7-6^5*4^3*(2+1)$
288237992	$98*((7^6*5-4)*(3+2)-1)$	301317297	$9^8*7-6^5*(4+32)$
288238188	$98*((7^6*5-4)*(3+2)+1)$	301317537	$9^8*7+6^5*(4-32)$
288241912	$98*((7^6*5+4)*(3+2)-1)$	301319373	$9^8*7+6^5*(5-4*32)$
288242108	$98*((7^6*5+4)*(3+2)+1)$	301319549	$9^8*7+(6-5^4*3)/21$
289669103	$(9+8)*((7+6)^5*4^3*2-1)$	301320180	$9^8*7-(6^5*4+3)*21$
289669137	$(9+8)*((7+6)^5*4^3*2+1)$	301320306	$9^8*7-(6^5*4-3)*21$
290966815	$9^8*7-(654/3)^2+1$	301320807	$9^8*7-6^5*4*(3+2)$
291229668	$9^8*(7-(6/5/4^3)^{-2}+1)$	301321371	$9^8*7-6*(5^4+32)$
294004753	$98*(7^6*(54-3)/2-1)$	301321392	$9^8*7-6^5*(4^3*2+1)$
294004949	$98*(7^6*(54-3)/2+1)$	301321522	$9^8*7-6^5*(4^3+2)$
294590279	$(-9+8*7^6)*((5^4+3)/2-1)$	301321524	$9^8*7-(6^5*4+3)*21$
294595913	$(9+8*7^6)*((5^4+3)/2-1)$	301321650	$9^8*7-(6^5*4-3)*21$
295416567	$9*(-8+7^6*(5+4)*(32-1))$	301321815	$9^8*7-6^5*(3^2-1)$
295416711	$9*(8+7^6*(5+4)*(32-1))$	301322232	$9^8*7-(6+5^4)*32$
296474913	$(-9+8*7^6*5)*(4^3-2+1)$	301322284	$9^8*7-(6+5)*4^3*(4+32)$
296476047	$(9+8*7^6*5)*(4^3-2+1)$	301322306	$9^8*7-(6+5)*(4^3-1)$
296544015	$9^8*(7-6/54)^{-3*21}$	301322367	$9^8*7+6^5*4*(3-21)$
296544141	$9^8*(7-6/54)^{3*21}$	301323212	$9^8*7+6^5*(4-3*21)$
296580316	$9^8+7^6*5*(4^3-1)$	301323472	$9^8*7-(6+5)*4^3*(4+32)$
297756806	$9^8+7^6*5*(4^3+1)$	301323783	$9^8*7-6*(5^4+2-1)$
297960039	$9^8*7-6^5*(4^3+1)$	301323795	$9^8*7-6*(5^4-2+1)$
297975591	$9^8*7-6^5*(4^3-1)$	301324057	$9^8*7-6^5*(4^3+2+1)$
298004900	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5+(4*3)^2)-1)$	301324187	$9^8*7-6^5*(4^3+2-1)$
298004934	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5+(4*3)^2)+1)$	301324317	$9^8*7-6^5*(4^3-2+1)$
298020177	$9^8*7-(6+5^4*3)*21$	301324338	$9^8*7-(6+5^4*3)*21$
298020429	$9^8*7+(6-5^4*3)*21$	301324419	$9^8*7-6*(5+4^3+1)$
298345175	$-9-8*(7^6-5)*(4-32)$	301324431	$9^8*7-6^5*(3+2-1)$
298345193	$9-8*(7^6-5)*(4-32)$	301324479	$9^8*7+6*(5-4^3-1)$
298356288	$9-(8*7^6-5)*(4-32)$	301324491	$9^8*7+6*(5-4^3+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
301324758	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 654 \cdot (3+2^{\wedge} - 1)$	301337421	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (54 \cdot 32 + 1)$
301324770	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (65+4) \cdot (32+1)$	301337961	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6 \cdot 5 + 4) \cdot 321$
301324800	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (6+5-4) \cdot 321$	301339977	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot 5 \cdot (432-1)$
301324908	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (65+4) \cdot (32-1)$	301340001	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (5 \cdot 432-1)$
301325034	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (65-4) \cdot (32+1)$	301340013	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (5 \cdot 432+1)$
301325223	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 6 \cdot (5^{\wedge} 4 - 321)$	301340037	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot 5 \cdot (432+1)$
301325241	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (5 \cdot 4 - 321)$	301341171	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6+5) \cdot 4 \cdot 321$
301325292	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 65 \cdot (4-32+1)$	301342356	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6/54)^{\wedge} - 3 \cdot 21$
301325391	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (65+4) \cdot (3+21)$	301344381	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (5+4) \cdot 321$
301325442	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (6-5+4) \cdot 321$	301386075	$9^8 \cdot (7 + (6/54)^{\wedge} 3) - 21$
301325514	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (6 \cdot 5 + 43) \cdot 21$	301386117	$9^8 \cdot (7 + (6/54)^{\wedge} 3) + 21$
301325559	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6-54) \cdot (32-1)$	301414407	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 65 \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 21$
301325631	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 6 \cdot (5 \cdot 43 + 21)$	301447167	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 65 \cdot (43^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
301325654	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (65+4/3) \cdot 21$	301447297	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 65 \cdot (43^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
301325661	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (65+4-3) \cdot 21$	301489440	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6^{\wedge} 5 - 43) \cdot 21$
301325710	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (65-4/3) \cdot 21$	301491246	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6^{\wedge} 5 + 43) \cdot 21$
301325883	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 6 \cdot (5 \cdot 43 - 21)$	301525746	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (6-5^{\wedge} 4) \cdot 321$
301326123	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (6-5+43) \cdot 21$	301529598	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6+5^{\wedge} 4) \cdot 321$
301326453	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 6 \cdot (5 \cdot 4 \cdot (3+2) - 1)$	301951071	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6^{\wedge} 5 / 4 \cdot 321$
301326537	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 6 \cdot (54+32-1)$	302071263	$-9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5 \cdot 4) \cdot 321$
301327557	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (54+32-1)$	302071281	$9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5 \cdot 4) \cdot 321$
301327641	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (5 \cdot 4 \cdot (3+2) - 1)$	302099511	$-9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5 \cdot 4) \cdot 321$
301327971	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6-5+43) \cdot 21$	302099529	$9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5 \cdot 4) \cdot 321$
301328211	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (5 \cdot 43 - 21)$	302108499	$-9+(8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5) - 4) \cdot 321$
301328384	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (65-4/3) \cdot 21$	302108517	$9+(8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5) - 4) \cdot 321$
301328433	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (65+4-3) \cdot 21$	302111067	$-9+(8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5) + 4) \cdot 321$
301328440	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (65+4/3) \cdot 21$	302111085	$9+(8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5) + 4) \cdot 321$
301328463	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (5 \cdot 43 + 21)$	302116203	$-9+(8 \cdot 7^{\wedge} 6 - 5 \cdot 4) \cdot 321$
301328535	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (6-54) \cdot (32-1)$	302116221	$9+(8 \cdot 7^{\wedge} 6 - 5 \cdot 4) \cdot 321$
301328580	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6 \cdot 5 + 43) \cdot 21$	302119413	$-9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5/4) \cdot 321$
301328652	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6-5+4) \cdot 321$	302119431	$9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5/4) \cdot 321$
301328703	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (65+4) \cdot (3+21)$	302120055	$-9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5+4) \cdot 321$
301328802	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 65 \cdot (4-32+1)$	302120073	$9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5+4) \cdot 321$
301328853	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 6 \cdot (5 \cdot 4 - 321)$	302125191	$-9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5 - 4) \cdot 321$
301328871	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (5^{\wedge} 4 - 321)$	302125209	$9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5 - 4) \cdot 321$
301329060	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (65-4) \cdot (32+1)$	302125833	$-9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5/4) \cdot 321$
301329186	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (65+4) \cdot (32-1)$	302125851	$9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5/4) \cdot 321$
301329294	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6+5-4) \cdot 321$	302129043	$-9+(8 \cdot 7^{\wedge} 6 + 5 \cdot 4) \cdot 321$
301329324	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (65+4) \cdot (32+1)$	302129061	$9+(8 \cdot 7^{\wedge} 6 + 5 \cdot 4) \cdot 321$
301329336	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 654 \cdot (3+2^{\wedge} - 1)$	302134179	$-9+(8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5) - 4) \cdot 321$
301329603	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 6 \cdot (5-432+1)$	302134197	$9+(8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5) - 4) \cdot 321$
301329615	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 6 \cdot (5-432-1)$	302136747	$-9+(8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5) + 4) \cdot 321$
301329663	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 654 \cdot (3+2-1)$	302136765	$9+(8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5) + 4) \cdot 321$
301329675	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (5+432+1)$	302145735	$-9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5+4) \cdot 321$
301329756	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (65+4^{\wedge} 3) \cdot 21$	302145753	$9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5+4) \cdot 321$
301329777	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 65 \cdot (43-2+1)$	302173983	$-9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5 \cdot 4) \cdot 321$
301329907	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 65 \cdot (43+2-1)$	302174001	$9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5 \cdot 4) \cdot 321$
301330037	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 65 \cdot (43+2+1)$	302271705	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (54^{\wedge} 3 - 21)$
301330299	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (543-2+1)$	302271957	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (54^{\wedge} 3 + 21)$
301330311	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (543+2-1)$	302508027	$9^8 \cdot ((7+6)/(5+4))^{\wedge} 3 \cdot 2+1)$
301330622	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6+5) \cdot (4+321)$	303096135	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (543^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
301330882	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 65 \cdot (4-3 \cdot 21)$	303096147	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (543^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
301331727	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 65 \cdot 4 \cdot (3-21)$	303299113	$-9+8 \cdot 7^{\wedge} 6 \cdot (5/4+321)$
301331788	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6+5) \cdot (432-1)$	303299131	$9+8 \cdot 7^{\wedge} 6 \cdot (5/4+321)$
301331810	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6+5) \cdot (432+1)$	303317055	$9/(8 \cdot 7/(6/(5^{\wedge} 4 - 3)))^{\wedge} - 2 - 1$
301331862	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6+5+4) \cdot 321$	303317057	$9/(8 \cdot 7/(6/(5^{\wedge} 4 - 3)))^{\wedge} - 2 + 1$
301332279	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 654 \cdot (3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	303727623	$-9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5^{\wedge} 4) \cdot 321$
301332444	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (65 \cdot 4 - 3) \cdot 21$	303727641	$9+8 \cdot (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5^{\wedge} 4) \cdot 321$
301332570	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (65 \cdot 4 + 3) \cdot 21$	303792039	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 6^{\wedge} 5 \cdot (4-321)$
301332572	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 65 \cdot (4^{\wedge} 3 + 21)$	303854247	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6^{\wedge} 5 \cdot (4+321)$
301332702	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 65 \cdot (43 \cdot 2 + 1)$	303887295	$9 \cdot (-8+7^{\wedge} 6 \cdot ((5+4) \cdot 32-1))$
301332723	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (5^{\wedge} 4 + 321)$	303887439	$9 \cdot (8+7^{\wedge} 6 \cdot ((5+4) \cdot 32-1))$
301333287	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 65 \cdot 4 \cdot (3+21)$	303904911	$-9+87 \cdot ((6-5^{\wedge} 4 \cdot 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
301333788	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6 \cdot 54 - 3) \cdot 21$	303904929	$9+87 \cdot ((6-5^{\wedge} 4 \cdot 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
301333914	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6 \cdot 54 + 3) \cdot 21$	303905085	$-9+87 \cdot ((6-5^{\wedge} 4 \cdot 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
301334545	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (6-54^{\wedge} 3) / 21$	303905103	$9+87 \cdot ((6-5^{\wedge} 4 \cdot 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
301334721	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 6 \cdot (5-4 \cdot 321)$	304633665	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (6-54^{\wedge} 3) \cdot 21$
301336557	$9^8 \cdot 7 - 6 \cdot 5 \cdot (4-321)$	304633917	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6+54^{\wedge} 3) \cdot 21$
301336797	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot 5 \cdot (4+321)$	304678503	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6^{\wedge} 5 \cdot (432-1)$
301336821	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot 5 \cdot 43 \cdot (2+1)$	304694055	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6^{\wedge} 5 \cdot (432+1)$
301336980	$9^8 \cdot 7 + (6+5) \cdot 43 \cdot 21$	304946127	$9 \cdot (-8+7^{\wedge} 6 \cdot (5+4) \cdot 32-1)$
301337409	$9^8 \cdot 7 + 6 \cdot (54 \cdot 32-1)$	304946145	$9 \cdot (-8+7^{\wedge} 6 \cdot (5+4) \cdot 32+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
304948503	$9 * ((8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5+4)) * 32 - 1)$	335666934	$9 * (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5)) * (4 - 321))$
304948521	$9 * ((8+7^{\wedge}6 * (5+4)) * 32 + 1)$	337919991	$-9 + (8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge} - 4 * (32 + 1)$
305534355	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43/2) - 1)$	337920009	$9 + (8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge} - 4 * (32 + 1)$
305534551	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5+43/2) + 1)$	338082264	$9 * (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 321)$
305854668	$9 * (87 * (-6 + 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)) - 1)$	338082408	$9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 321)$
305854686	$9 * (87 * (-6 + 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)) + 1)$	338671008	$(-9 + 876) * (5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) - 1)$
305864064	$9 * (87 * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)) - 1)$	338671874	$(-9 + 876) * 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) - 1$
305864082	$9 * (87 * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)) + 1)$	338671876	$(-9 + 876) * 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) + 1$
305874391	$-9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 + 321)$	338672742	$(-9 + 876) * (5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) + 1)$
305874409	$9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 + 321)$	338705064	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 - 6^{\wedge} - 5 * 4^{\wedge}(3+2) + 1)$
305885766	$-9 + (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 + 321)$	338824493	$9 * ((-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * 4^{\wedge}3 - 2) - 1$
305885784	$9 + (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 + 321)$	338824495	$9 * ((-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) / 4^{\wedge} - 3 - 2) + 1$
305886815	$(-9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1)$	338824529	$9 * ((-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * 4^{\wedge}3 + 2) - 1$
305887985	$(9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1)$	338824531	$9 * ((-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * 4^{\wedge}3 + 2) + 1$
305889016	$-9 + (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 + 321)$	338824701	$9 * ((-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * 4^{\wedge}3 + 21)$
305889034	$9 + (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 + 321)$	338828859	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 - 21)$
305900391	$-9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 + 321)$	338829237	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 + 21)$
305900409	$9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 + 321)$	338833539	$9 * ((8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * 4^{\wedge}3 - 21)$
307819911	$-9 + 87 * ((6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	338833709	$9 * ((8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) / 4^{\wedge} - 3 - 2) - 1$
307819929	$9 + 87 * ((6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	338833711	$9 * ((8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) / 4^{\wedge} - 3 - 2) + 1$
307820085	$-9 + 87 * ((6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	338833747	$9 * ((8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) / 4^{\wedge} - 3 + 2) + 1$
307820103	$9 + 87 * ((6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	338833917	$9 * ((8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * 4^{\wedge}3 + 21)$
311298960	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5+4) * 3 - 2 - 1)$	339687999	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * (2 + 1)$
311299009	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 54 - 3) / 2 - 1)$	339770214	$98 * ((7 + 6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
311299205	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 54 - 3) / 2 + 1)$	339770410	$98 * ((7 + 6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
311299303	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 54 + 3) / 2 - 1)$	339789249	$9 * (8^{\wedge}7 * 6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * (2 + 1)$
311299499	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 54 + 3) / 2 + 1)$	339830109	$9 * (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4) * 321)$
311299548	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5+4) * 3 + 2 + 1)$	339830253	$9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4) * 321)$
311424426	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 + (6/5/4 * 3)^{\wedge} - 2 - 1)$	339861888	$9 * (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 321)$
311687279	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 + (654/3)^{\wedge} (2 + 1))$	339862032	$9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 321)$
314475705	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5+4) * (32 + 1))$	339885000	$9 * (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * 321)$
314475849	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5+4) * (32 + 1))$	339885144	$9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * 321)$
316593387	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3 - 21))$	339885384	$-9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4)) * 321$
316593531	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3 - 21))$	339885402	$-9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4)) * 321$
317063957	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4 + 3/2) - 1)$	339890520	$-9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4)) * 321$
317064153	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4 + 3/2) + 1)$	339890538	$9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4)) * 321$
317439991	$-9 + (8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge} - 4 * (32 - 1)$	339890778	$9 * (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * 321)$
317440009	$9 + (8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge} - 4 * (32 - 1)$	339890922	$9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * 321)$
318504717	$9^{\wedge}(8 + 7) / 6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	339913890	$9 * (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * 321)$
318505203	$9^{\wedge}(8 + 7) / 6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	339914034	$9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * 321)$
318711069	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 * 4 - 321))$	339945669	$9 * (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) * 321)$
318711213	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 * 4 - 321))$	339945813	$9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) * 321)$
320005263	$(9 + 8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 / 2 - 1)$	340123161	$-98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3) / 2 + 1)$
320005297	$(9 + 8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / (4^{\wedge} - 3 * 2) + 1)$	340123357	$-98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3) / 2 - 1)$
320790384	$(9 + 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 543) * (2 + 1)$	340594632	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 - (6 / (5 + 4))^{\wedge} (3 * 2) + 1)$
321698952	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 - 6^{\wedge} - 5 * 4^{\wedge} (3 * 2) + 1)$	341693514	$9 * (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 321)$
322560000	$9 * (8^{\wedge}(7 / -6) / 5)^{\wedge} - 4 * (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	341693658	$9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 321)$
322815038	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 - 32) + 1)$	342186615	$-9 + 876 * (5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) - 1)$
322815234	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 - 32) - 1)$	342186633	$9 + 876 * (5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) - 1)$
322820883	$9^{\wedge}8 * ((7 + 6 - (5 + 4)^{\wedge} - 3) / 2 + 1)$	342187490	$-9 + 876 * 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) - 1$
322842478	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 - 32) + 1)$	342187492	$-9 + 876 * 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) + 1$
322842674	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 - 32) - 1)$	342187508	$9 + 876 * 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) - 1$
322879932	$9^{\wedge}8 * ((7 + 6 + (5 + 4)^{\wedge} - 3) / 2 + 1)$	342187510	$9 + 876 * 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) + 1$
328593559	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (54 + 3) / 2 - 1)$	342188367	$-9 + 876 * (5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) + 1)$
328593755	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (54 + 3) / 2 + 1)$	342188385	$9 + 876 * (5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) + 1)$
329269024	$98 * ((7 * 6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	342328994	$98 * (-7 + (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
329269220	$98 * ((7 * 6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	342329190	$98 * (-7 + (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
329299478	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) / 2) - 1$	342330366	$98 * (7 + (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
329299480	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) / 2) + 1$	342330562	$98 * (7 + (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
329299622	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) / 2) - 1$	343146479	$(9 + 8) * (7 * (6 + 5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
329299624	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) / 2) + 1$	343146513	$(9 + 8) * (7 * (6 + 5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
332386821	$9^{\wedge}8 * ((7 / (6 / (5 * 4) - 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	343254024	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 - (6 / (5 + 4))^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
332476001	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 2) - 1$	344108628	$9 * (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 + 321))$
332476003	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 2) + 1$	344108772	$9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 + 321))$
332476145	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 2) - 1$	344137878	$9 * (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 + 321))$
332476147	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 2) + 1$	344138022	$9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 + 321))$
333965184	$-98 * ((7 + 6) * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1)$	344163750	$98 * ((7 - 6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
333977728	$98 * ((7 + 6) * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1)$	344163946	$98 * ((7 - 6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
333977924	$98 * ((7 + 6) * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1)$	344337144	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7 * 654) * (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
335638260	$-9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 - 321))$	344340936	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76 * 54) * (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
335638404	$9 * (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 - 321))$	344349288	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 765 * 4) * (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
335666790	$-9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 - 321))$	344370852	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 - (6 / (5 + 4))^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
344372238	$(9^8 - 765/4) * (3^2 - 1)$	364225833	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5) * 43 + 2 - 1)$
344372484	$9^8 * (7 + 6 - 5) - 4 * 321$	364225851	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5) * 43 + 2 + 1)$
344372865	$9^8 * (7 + 6 - 5) - 43 * 21$	364225860	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 - 5) * 43 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
344373169	$9 - 8 * (76 - (5 + 4)^{\wedge} (3^2 - 1))$	364225959	$9 * (8 * ((7^6 - 5) * 43 + 2) - 1)$
344374367	$-9 + 8 * (76 + (5 + 4)^{\wedge} (3^2 - 1))$	364225977	$9 * (8 * ((7^6 - 5) * 43 + 2) + 1)$
344374671	$9^8 * (7 + 6 - 5) + 43 * 21$	364226013	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5) * 43 + 21)$
344375052	$9^8 * (7 + 6 - 5) + 4 * 321$	364227336	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 - 5) * 43 + 21)$
344375298	$(9^8 + 765/4) * (3^2 - 1)$	364239180	$9 * ((8 * 7^6 - 5) * 43 - 21)$
344376684	$9^8 * (7 + (6 / (5 + 4)^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	364239558	$9 * ((8 * 7^6 - 5) * 43 + 21)$
344377413	$((9^8 + 7 * 65) * 4 + 3) * 2 - 1$	364243050	$9 * ((8 * 7^6 + 5) * 43 - 21)$
344398248	$(9^8 + 765 * 4) * (3^2 - 1)$	364243428	$9 * ((8 * 7^6 + 5) * 43 + 21)$
344406600	$(9^8 + 76 * 54) * (3^2 - 1)$	364255272	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 + 5) * 43 - 21)$
344410392	$(9^8 + 7 * 654) * (3^2 - 1)$	364256595	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5) * 43 - 21)$
344898750	$98 * ((7 - 6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	364256631	$9 * (8 * ((7^6 + 5) * 43 - 2) - 1)$
344898946	$98 * ((7 - 6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	364256649	$9 * (8 * ((7^6 + 5) * 43 - 2) + 1)$
345001386	$-9^{\wedge} (8 + 7 - 6) + 5^{\wedge} (4 * 3) * (2 + 1)$	364256748	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 + 5) * 43 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
345493512	$9^8 * (7 + (6 / (5 + 4)^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	364256757	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5) * 43 - 2 - 1)$
345702240	$(9 + 876) * (5^{\wedge} 4^{\wedge} (3/2) - 1)$	364256775	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5) * 43 - 2 + 1)$
345703124	$(9 + 876) * 5^{\wedge} 4^{\wedge} (3/2) - 1$	364256793	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5) * 43 + 2 - 1)$
345703126	$(9 + 876) * 5^{\wedge} 4^{\wedge} (3/2) + 1$	364256811	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5) * 43 + 2 + 1)$
345704010	$(9 + 876) * (5^{\wedge} 4^{\wedge} (3/2) + 1)$	364256820	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 + 5) * 43 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
346738994	$98 * (-7 + (6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	364256919	$9 * (8 * ((7^6 + 5) * 43 + 2) - 1)$
346739190	$98 * (-7 + (6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	364256937	$9 * (8 * ((7^6 + 5) * 43 + 2) + 1)$
346740366	$98 * (7 + (6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	364256973	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5) * 43 + 21)$
346740562	$98 * (7 + (6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	364258296	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 + 5) * 43 + 21)$
347285016	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 - 5) * (43 - 2) - 1)$	366987166	$98 * ((7^6 - 5^{\wedge} 4) * 32 - 1)$
347285079	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5) * (43 - 2) - 1)$	366987362	$98 * ((7^6 - 5^{\wedge} 4) * 32 + 1)$
347285097	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5) * (43 - 2) + 1)$	368884446	$98 * ((7^6 - 5^{\wedge} 4) * 32 - 1)$
347285160	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 - 5) * (43 - 2) + 1)$	368884642	$98 * ((7^6 - 5^{\wedge} 4) * 32 + 1)$
347314536	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 + 5) * (43 - 2) - 1)$	368918942	$98 * ((7^6 - 5 - 4) * 32 - 1)$
347314599	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5) * (43 - 2) - 1)$	368919138	$98 * ((7^6 - 5 - 4) * 32 + 1)$
347314617	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5) * (43 - 2) + 1)$	368931486	$98 * ((7^6 - 5) * 4^{\wedge} 3 / 2 - 1)$
347314680	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 + 5) * (43 - 2) + 1)$	368931682	$98 * ((7^6 - 5) * 4^{\wedge} 3 / 2 + 1)$
347822500	$(9 / (8 + 7 * (6 - (5^{\wedge} 4)^{\wedge} 3)))^{\wedge} 2 - 1$	368943246	$98 * ((7^6 - 5/4) * 32 - 1)$
348241031	$-9 + 8 * 7^6 / 5 * (43^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	368943442	$98 * ((7^6 - 5/4) * 32 + 1)$
348241049	$9 + 8 * 7^6 / 5 * (43^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	368944030	$98 * ((7^6 - 5 + 4) * 32 - 1)$
348867684	$(9 / (8 - 7 * (6 + (5^{\wedge} 4)^{\wedge} 3)))^{\wedge} 2 - 1$	368944226	$98 * ((7^6 - 5 + 4) * 32 + 1)$
349325214	$98 * ((7 + 6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	368950302	$98 * ((7^6 + 5 - 4) * 32 - 1)$
349325410	$98 * ((7 + 6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	368950498	$98 * ((7^6 + 5 - 4) * 32 + 1)$
349839981	$(-9 * 87 + (6^{\wedge} 5 / 4)^{\wedge} 3) / 21$	368951086	$98 * ((7^6 + 5/4) * 32 - 1)$
350042472	$9^8 * (7 + 6^{\wedge} - 5 * 4^{\wedge} (3 + 2) + 1)$	368951282	$98 * ((7^6 + 5/4) * 32 + 1)$
352321293	$9 + (8^{\wedge} (7 + 6 - 5) - 4 * 3) * 21$	368962846	$98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4^{\wedge} 3 / 2 - 1)$
352321509	$(-9 + 8^{\wedge} (7 + 6 - 5) * (4 + 3)) * (2 + 1)$	368963042	$98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4^{\wedge} 3 / 2 + 1)$
352321517	$9 + (8^{\wedge} (7 + 6 - 5) - 4 / 3) * 21$	368975390	$98 * ((7^6 + 5 + 4) * 32 - 1)$
352321563	$(9 + 8^{\wedge} (7 + 6 - 5) * (4 + 3)) * (2 + 1)$	368975586	$98 * ((7^6 + 5 + 4) * 32 + 1)$
352321573	$9 + (8^{\wedge} (7 + 6 - 5) + 4 / 3) * 21$	369009886	$98 * ((7^6 + 5 * 4) * 32 - 1)$
352321797	$9 + (8^{\wedge} (7 + 6 - 5) + 4 * 3) * 21$	369010082	$98 * ((7^6 + 5 * 4) * 32 + 1)$
355770387	$(-9 + 8 * 7^6 * 54 / 3) * 21$	369622758	$(-9 + 8 * 7) * 6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge} 3 / 2 - 1)$
355770765	$(9 + 8 * 7^6 * 54 / 3) * 21$	369622993	$(-9 + 8 * 7) * (6 * 5 * 4^{\wedge} 3 / 2 - 1)$
357417564	$-98 * (7^6 * (5 - 4 - 32) + 1)$	369623087	$(-9 + 8 * 7) * (6 * 5 * 4^{\wedge} 3 / 2 + 1)$
357417760	$-98 * (7^6 * (5 - 4 - 32) - 1)$	369623322	$(-9 + 8 * 7) * 6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge} 3 / 2 + 1)$
358611624	$9 * (87 + 65) * (4^{\wedge} 3 / 2 - 1)$	370354642	$98 * (-7 + (6^{\wedge} 5 / 4)^{\wedge} (3 - 2 + 1))$
358614360	$9 * (87 + 65) * (4^{\wedge} 3 / 2 + 1)$	370356014	$98 * (7 + (6^{\wedge} 5 / 4)^{\wedge} (3 - 2 + 1))$
360005923	$(9 + 8) * (7^6 * 5 * 4 * 3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	370907166	$98 * ((7^6 + 5^{\wedge} 4) * 32 - 1)$
360005957	$(9 + 8) * (7^6 * 5 * 4 * 3^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	370907362	$98 * ((7^6 + 5^{\wedge} 4) * 32 + 1)$
360139024	$98 * ((7 * 6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	372795906	$(9^8 - 7^6 * 5 * 43) * 21$
360139220	$98 * ((7 * 6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	375073664	$(9 / (8 * 7 * (6^{\wedge} 5 - 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2))^{\wedge} - 1$
361064709	$9 * (-8 + 7^6 * (5 * 4 + 321))$	377396096	$(9 / (8 * 7 * (6^{\wedge} 5 + 4 * 3)^{\wedge} 2))^{\wedge} - 1$
361064853	$9 * (8 + 7^6 * (5 * 4 + 321))$	377650401	$(-9 + 8 * 7^6 * 5 / 4) * 321$
363181671	$9 * (-87 + (6 + 5 - 4)^{\wedge} 3 / 2 - 1)$	377653299	$9 + 8 * 7^6 * 5 / 4 * 321$
363181689	$9 * (-87 + (6 + 5 - 4)^{\wedge} 3 / 2 + 1)$	377656179	$(9 + 8 * 7^6 * 5 / 4) * 321$
363182327	$9 * (-8 - 7 + (6 + 5 - 4)^{\wedge} 3 / 2) - 1$	379774300	$(-9 / (8 + 7 * (6 - (5^{\wedge} 4)^{\wedge} 3 * 2)))^{\wedge} - 1$
363182329	$9 * (-8 - 7 + (6 + 5 - 4)^{\wedge} 3 / 2) + 1$	380476768	$98 * (7^6 * (5 - 4 + 32) - 1)$
363182966	$9 * (8 * 7 + (6 + 5 - 4)^{\wedge} 3 / 2) - 1$	380476964	$98 * (7^6 * (5 - 4 + 32) + 1)$
363182968	$9 * (8 * 7 + (6 + 5 - 4)^{\wedge} 3 / 2) + 1$	381166488	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 - 5) * (43 + 2) - 1)$
364224312	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 - 5) * 43 - 21)$	381166551	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5) * (43 + 2) - 1)$
364225635	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5) * 43 - 21)$	381166569	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5) * (43 + 2) + 1)$
364225671	$9 * (8 * ((7^6 - 5) * 43 - 2) - 1)$	381166632	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 - 5) * (43 + 2) + 1)$
364225689	$9 * (8 * ((7^6 - 5) * 43 - 2) + 1)$	381184794	$9 * ((8 * 7^6 + 5) * (43 + 2) + 1)$
364225788	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 - 5) * 43 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	381198888	$9 * 8 * ((7^6 + 5) * (43 + 2) - 1)$
364225797	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5) * 43 - 2 - 1)$	381198951	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5) * (43 + 2) - 1)$
364225815	$9 * (8 * (7^6 - 5) * 43 - 2 + 1)$	381198969	$9 * (8 * (7^6 + 5) * (43 + 2) + 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
381199032	$9*8*((7^6+5)*(43+2)+1)$	407518807	$-9+8*(7^6-5)*(432+1)$
382934682	$9^8+7^6*(5+4)*321$	407518825	$9+8*(7^6-5)*(432+1)$
386109764	$9^8(8+7-6)-5*(4^3+2+1)$	407533962	$-9+(8*7^6-5)*(432+1)$
386109774	$9^8(8+7-6)-5*(4^3+2-1)$	407533980	$9+(8*7^6-5)*(432+1)$
387414239	$9^8(8+7-6)-5^4*(3^2+1)$	407538292	$-9+(8*7^6+5)*(432+1)$
387415489	$9^8(8+7-6)-5^4*(3^2-1)$	407538310	$9+(8*7^6+5)*(432+1)$
387417989	$9^8(8+7-6)-5^4*(3+2-1)$	407553447	$-9+8*(7^6+5)*(432+1)$
387418605	$9^8(8+7-6)-(5^4+3)*(2+1)$	407553465	$9+8*(7^6+5)*(432+1)$
387418623	$9^8(8+7-6)-(5^4-3)*(2+1)$	411300887	$-9+8*(7^6*(5+432)-1)$
387422355	$9^8(8+7-6)+(5^4-3)*(2+1)$	411300903	$-9+8*(7^6*(5+432)+1)$
387422373	$9^8(8+7-6)+(5^4+3)*(2+1)$	411300905	$9+8*(7^6*(5+432)-1)$
387422989	$9^8(8+7-6)+5^4*(3+2-1)$	411300921	$9+8*(7^6*(5+432)+1)$
387425489	$9^8(8+7-6)+5^4*(3^2-1)$	413350236	$9*876/5*(4^3+2+1)$
387426739	$9^8(8+7-6)+5^4*(3^2+1)$	415047934	$98*((7^6-5)*4^3+2-1)$
388731204	$9^8(8+7-6)+5*(4^3+2-1)$	415048130	$98*((7^6-5)*4^3+2+1)$
388731214	$9^8(8+7-6)+5*(4^3+2+1)$	415083214	$98*((7^6+5)*4^3+2-1)$
389191976	$9*((8+7^6(-6+5+4))^3+2)-1$	415083410	$98*((7^6+5)*4^3+2+1)$
391637970	$9*(-8+7^6/5)*(43^2+1)$	415686142	$(9+8)*(7*(6-5^4+3)^2-1)$
391771098	$9*(-8+7^6/5*(43^2+1))$	415686176	$(9+8)*(7*(6-5^4+3)^2+1)$
391771242	$9*(8+7^6/5*(43^2+1))$	417712626	$9^8*(7-(6/(5+4)))^3+2+1$
391904370	$9*(8+7^6/5)*(43^2+1)$	421041142	$(9+8)*(7*(6+5^4+3)^2-1)$
394569135	$9^8*7+654^3/(2+1)$	421041176	$(9+8)*(7*(6+5^4+3)^2+1)$
397517868	$9^8*(7+(6/5/4^3))^2+1$	422495595	$9^8*(76/54+3)^2+1$
397771171	$98*(7^6*(5+4^3)/2-1)$	423418653	$-98+7^6*(5^4+3)^2-1$
397771367	$98*(7^6*(5+4^3)/2+1)$	423418823	$9*8+7^6*(5^4+3)^2-1$
399504366	$9^8*(7+6)-543^2(2+1)$	423418849	$98+7^6*(5^4+3)^2-1$
400006609	$9+8*7^6*5*(4^3+2+1)$	423653951	$-98+7^6*(5^4+3)^2+1$
400240386	$9*(-8+7^6*54/3)*21$	423654121	$9*8+7^6*(5^4+3)^2+1$
400241205	$(9+(8-7^6*54)*3)^2-21$	423654147	$98+7^6*(5^4+3)^2+1$
400241385	$-9-(8-7^6*54)*3*21$	423698727	$-9*(8-7/((6^5+4)/3))^2-1$
400241403	$9-(8-7^6*54)*3*21$	423698729	$-9*(8-7/((6^5+4)/3))^2+1$
400241583	$(9-(8-7^6*54)*3)*21$	423698871	$9*(8+7/((6^5+4)/3))^2-1$
400242213	$(-9+(8+7^6*54)*3)*21$	423698873	$9*(8+7/((6^5+4)/3))^2+1$
400242393	$-9+(8+7^6*54)*3*21$	425684220	$9^8*(7-6/54+3)-21$
400242411	$9+(8+7^6*54)*3*21$	425684262	$9^8*(7-6/54+3)+21$
400242591	$(9+(8+7^6*54)*3)*21$	426595176	$98*(7^6*(5+4^3/2)-1)$
400243410	$9*(8+7^6*54/3)*21$	426595372	$98*(7^6*(5+4^3/2)+1)$
401888967	$-9-8*(7^6*(5-432)+1)$	428605113	$(-9+8*7^6*(5^4+3)^2-1)$
401888983	$-9-8*(7^6*(5-432)-1)$	428605767	$(-9+8*7^6*(5^4+3)^2+1)$
401888985	$9-8*(7^6*(5-432)+1)$	430006738	$(9+8)*(7^6*5^4+3-21)$
401889001	$9-8*(7^6*(5-432)-1)$	430007452	$(9+8)*(7^6*5^4+3+21)$
402653097	$9+(8^7+6-5)-4*(3+2+1)$	430421430	$(9^8-7^6*54)*(3^2+1)$
402653289	$9+(8^7+6-5)+4*(3+2+1)$	430426170	$(9^8-7^6*54)*(3^2+1)$
403367928	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4)^3/21)$	430436610	$(9^8-7^6*54)*(3^2+1)$
403368072	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4)^3/21)$	430466889	$9^8*(7-6+5+4)-321$
403535776	$98*(7^6*5*(4+3)-2-1)$	430467531	$9^8*(7-6+5+4)+321$
403536021	$98*(7^6*5*(4+3)-2^2-1)$	430467715	$((9^8+7^6)*5+43)^2-1$
403536119	$98*(7^6*5*(4+3)+2^2-1)$	430497810	$(9^8+7^6*54)*(3^2+1)$
403536364	$98*(7^6*5*(4+3)+2+1)$	430508250	$(9^8+7^6*54)*(3^2+1)$
405636503	$-9+8*(7^6-5)*(432-1)$	430512990	$(9^8+7^6*54)*(3^2+1)$
405636521	$9+8*(7^6-5)*(432-1)$	432006975	$9*(8*(7^6*(54-3)-2)-1)$
405651588	$-9+(8*7^6-5)*(432-1)$	432006993	$9*(8*(7^6*(54-3)-2)+1)$
405651606	$9+(8*7^6-5)*(432-1)$	432007092	$9*8*(7^6*(54-3)-2^2-1)$
405653761	$9^8/7^6-6*(5^4+3)^2+1$	432007164	$9*8*(7^6*(54-3)+2^2-1)$
405655898	$-9+(8*7^6+5)*(432-1)$	432007263	$9*(8*(7^6*(54-3)+2)-1)$
405655916	$9+(8*7^6+5)*(432-1)$	432007281	$9*(8*(7^6*(54-3)+2)+1)$
405670983	$-9+8*(7^6+5)*(432-1)$	432155317	$((9+8)/(7+(6^5/4)^3-2))^2-1$
405671001	$9+8*(7^6+5)*(432-1)$	435147835	$(-9+8^7/6)*(5^4+3)^2+1$
406577647	$-9+8*((7^6-5)*432-1)$	435170245	$(9+8^7/6)*(5^4+3)^2+1$
406577663	$-9+8*((7^6-5)*432+1)$	435250158	$9^8*(7+6/54+3)-21$
406577665	$9+8*((7^6-5)*432-1)$	435250200	$9^8*(7+6/54+3)+21$
406577681	$9+8*((7^6-5)*432+1)$	437682287	$(-98+7^6*5^4+43)/21$
406594791	$9*(8*(7^6*(5+43)-2)-1)$	438040953	$(-9+8*7^6*5^4*(4^3+2)-1)$
406594809	$9*(8*(7^6*(5+43)-2)+1)$	438044295	$(-9+8*7^6*5^4*(4^3+2)+1)$
406594908	$9*8*(7^6*(5+43)-2^2-1)$	438124827	$-98*(7^6*(5-43)+2^2-1)$
406594980	$9*8*(7^6*(5+43)+2^2-1)$	438124925	$-98*(7^6*(5-43)-2^2-1)$
406595079	$9*(8*(7^6*(5+43)+2)-1)$	439342031	$(-9+8^7/6)*((5^4+3)^2+1)$
406595097	$9*(8*(7^6*(5+43)+2)+1)$	439364657	$(9+8^7/6)*((5^4+3)^2+1)$
406612207	$-9+8*((7^6+5)*432-1)$	441066003	$-98+7^6*(5^4+3)^2-1$
406612223	$-9+8*((7^6+5)*432+1)$	441066199	$98+7^6*(5^4+3)^2-1$
406612225	$9+8*((7^6+5)*432-1)$	441301301	$-98+7^6*(5^4+3)^2+1$
406612241	$9+8*((7^6+5)*432+1)$	441301497	$98+7^6*(5^4+3)^2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
442759527	$(9+8*7^6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	461184178	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/4^*32+1)$
442762905	$(9+8*7^6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	461654604	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+432-1))$
443221794	$9^{\wedge}8*(7+(6/(5+4))^{\wedge}3+2+1)$	461654748	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+432-1))$
444713229	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2)+1)$	462323232	$(9/8/(7^*6*543)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
450007353	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3+21))$	462421918	$98*((7+6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
450007497	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3+21))$	462422114	$98*((7+6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
451066194	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-432+1))$	462713436	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+432)-1)$
451066338	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-432+1))$	462713454	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+432)+1)$
452125026	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-432)+1)$	462713580	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+432)-1)$
452125044	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-432)-1)$	462713598	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+432)+1)$
452125170	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-432)-1)$	463772286	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+432+1))$
452125188	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-432)+1)$	463772430	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+432+1))$
452198055	$(9+8*7^6)*(5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	466465472	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5*4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
452198745	$(9+8*7^6)*(5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	466700770	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5*4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
453183876	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-432-1))$	470478253	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*((5*4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
453184020	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-432-1))$	470478279	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5*4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
456209208	$9*8*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/21)$	470478423	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5*4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
456341004	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*432-1))$	470478449	$98+7^{\wedge}6*((5*4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
456341148	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*432-1))$	470713551	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*((5*4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
456379794	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*432-1))$	470713577	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5*4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
456379938	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*432-1))$	470713721	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5*4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
456478111	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	470713747	$98+7^{\wedge}6*((5*4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
456478129	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	472693494	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43-2)-1)$
457399791	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*432-1)$	472693690	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43-2)+1)$
457399809	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*432+1)$	472713584	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4+32)-1)$
457399935	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*432-1)$	472713780	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4+32)+1)$
457399953	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*432+1)$	472733674	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-2)-1)$
457416999	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54-32)-1)$	472733870	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-2)+1)$
457417017	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54-32)+1)$	473505516	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)*(4^*3-2+1)$
457418655	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	473511621	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6*5)*(4^*3-2+1)$
457418673	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	473516241	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6*5)*(4^*3-2+1)$
457418745	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6*54-3^*21)$	473522346	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)*(4^*3-2+1)$
457418907	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3)-21)$	474609132	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5^{\wedge}(4+3+2)-1)$
457418943	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3-2)-1)$	474609618	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5^{\wedge}(4+3+2)+1)$
457418961	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3-2)+1)$	476089488	$(9+8)*(7^*6)^{\wedge}5/(4+(3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$
457419015	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*54-32-1)$	481184312	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
457419033	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*54-32+1)$	481184338	$9*-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
457419087	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3)-2+1)$	481184482	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
457419105	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3)+2-1)$	481184508	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
457419123	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3)+2+1)$	481419610	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
457419150	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*54+3-21)$	481419636	$9*-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
457419195	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3/2)-1)$	481419780	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
457419222	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6*54-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	481419806	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
457419376	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3^{\wedge}2+1)$	481752082	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*((4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
457419402	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*54+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	481752108	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
457419429	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3/2)+1)$	481752252	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
457419474	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*54-3+21)$	481752278	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*((4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
457419501	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3)-2-1)$	481793032	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*((4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
457419519	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3)-2+1)$	481793058	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
457419537	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3)+2-1)$	481793202	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
457419591	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*54+32-1)$	481793228	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*((4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
457419609	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*54+32+1)$	481886199	$9*(8^{\wedge}7*(6+5^{\wedge}4/32)-1)$
457419663	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3+2)-1)$	481886217	$9*(8^{\wedge}7*(6+5^{\wedge}4/32)+1)$
457419681	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3+2)+1)$	481987370	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*((4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
457419717	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3)+21)$	481987396	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
457419879	$9*(8/7^{\wedge}6*54+3^*21)$	481987540	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
457419951	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	481987566	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*((4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
457419969	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	482028340	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*((4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
457421607	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54+32)-1)$	482028366	$9*-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*((4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
457421625	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54+32)+1)$	482028510	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
457438671	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*432-1)$	482028536	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*((4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
457438689	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*432+1)$	482360828	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
457438815	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*432-1)$	482360972	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$
457438833	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*432+1)$	482360998	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
458360495	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	482596126	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
458360513	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	482596270	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$
458458596	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432+1))$	482596296	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
458458740	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432+1))$	482831343	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)-2)-1)$
458497566	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432+1))$	482831361	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)-2)+1)$
458497710	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432+1))$	482831460	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$
458629416	$9*8*7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/21)$	482831532	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$
461183982	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/4^*32-1)$	482831631	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)+2)-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
482831649	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)+2)+1)$	514596069	$9*((-8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
484112822	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	514596087	$9*((-8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
484348120	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	514597365	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
488273365	$-9*876+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3*2-1$	514597383	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
488273367	$-9*876+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3*2+1$	515655495	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54*3^{\wedge}2+1))$
488280382	$9-876+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3*2-1$	515655639	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54*3^{\wedge}2+1))$
488280384	$9-876+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3*2+1$	518809942	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2)-1)$
488282134	$9+876+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3*2-1$	518810138	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2)+1)$
488282135	$9+876+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3*2^{\wedge}1$	518828464	$98*((7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
488282136	$9+876+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3*2+1$	518828660	$98*((7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
489457161	$9^{\wedge}8*(7/6*5/(4/3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	518831992	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
489987260	$98*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	518832188	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
490028910	$98*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	518835520	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*3^{\wedge}2-1$
492645786	$9^{\wedge}8*(76/(5+4)+3)-21$	518835716	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*3^{\wedge}2+1$
492645828	$9^{\wedge}8*(76/(5+4)+3)+21$	518854042	$98*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2)-1$
495028494	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)*(4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	518854238	$98*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2)+1$
495046089	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)*(4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	523158480	$(9-8/7*6)*((5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
495452087	$9*(-8+7*6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	524231131	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$
495452089	$9*(-8+7*6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	524466429	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
495452231	$9*(8+7*6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	524798901	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
495452233	$9*(8+7*6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	524839851	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
495751522	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*43-2-1)$	525034189	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$
495751718	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*43-2+1)$	525075159	$9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$
495751767	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	525407621	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
495751865	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	525642919	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$
495751914	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*43+2-1)$	528949895	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3*21)$
495752110	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*43+2+1)$	528949913	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3*21)$
495793662	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*43-2-1)$	531177822	$(9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*43)*-21$
495793858	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*43-2+1)$	531178002	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*43*21$
495793907	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	531178020	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*43*21$
495794005	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	531178200	$(9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*43)*21$
495794054	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*43+2-1)$	531184878	$(-9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5*43)*21$
495794250	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*43+2+1)$	531185058	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*43)*21$
497656152	$98*((7+6)*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	531185076	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*43)*21$
497656348	$98*((7+6)*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	531185214	$(-9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5*43)*21$
499771440	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+21)$	531185256	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5*43)*21$
499772933	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2)-1$	531185394	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*43)*21$
499772935	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2)+1$	531185412	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*43)*21$
499772969	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-2)-1$	531185592	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5*43)*21$
499772971	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-2)+1$	531192270	$(-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*43)*21$
499773141	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-21)$	531192450	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*43*21$
499774464	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-21)$	531192468	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*43*21$
501516372	$98*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	531192648	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*43)*21$
501559002	$98*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	536870840	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)*4)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
502211830	$(9^{\wedge}8*7/6*5+43)*2-1$	536870984	$(9+8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)*4)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
503317641	$9*((8+7)/(6/5)+4)*32+1)$	537851745	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+654^{\wedge}3*(2+1)$
503739243	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*54*3)*21$	538074450	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)*(4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
505979938	$-98+(7/(6-54^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2^{\wedge}1$	538093575	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)*(4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
505980019	$-9-8+(7/(6-54^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2^{\wedge}1$	542103363	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^{\wedge}3-21)$
505980053	$-9+8+(7/(6-54^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2^{\wedge}1$	542103741	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^{\wedge}3+21)$
505980134	$98+(7/(6-54^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2^{\wedge}1$	542123523	$9*((8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^{\wedge}3-21)$
508243437	$(-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*5*4)/3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	542123901	$9*((8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^{\wedge}3+21)$
508243535	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4*3-2)-1$	542129283	$9*((8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^{\wedge}3-21)$
508243537	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4*3-2)+1$	542129661	$9*((8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^{\wedge}3+21)$
508243823	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4*3+2)-1$	542149443	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^{\wedge}3-21)$
508243825	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4*3+2)+1$	542149821	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^{\wedge}3+21)$
508243923	$(9+8*7^{\wedge}6*5*4)/3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$	553420847	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)-2^{\wedge}-1)$
510218830	$9*((8+7)^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	553420945	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)+2^{\wedge}-1)$
510596651	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(543-2^{\wedge}-1)$	556300629	$9^{\wedge}8*(7+6)-54^{\wedge}3*21$
510596669	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(543-2^{\wedge}-1)$	557127315	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(-6*(5+4)^{\wedge}-3+2)-1)$
511067243	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*543-2^{\wedge}-1)$	557185655	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32-1)$
511067251	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*543+2^{\wedge}-1)$	557185673	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32-1)$
511067261	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*543-2^{\wedge}-1)$	558126839	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32)-1)$
511067269	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*543+2^{\wedge}-1)$	558126855	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32)+1)$
511180735	$(9*8-7)*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	558126857	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32)-1)$
511180865	$(9*8-7)*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	558126873	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32)+1)$
511537843	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(543+2^{\wedge}-1)$	559068039	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32+1)$
511537861	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(543+2^{\wedge}-1)$	559068057	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32+1)$
513525072	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5*4)^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	559406748	$9^{\wedge}8*(7+6)-5^{\wedge}4*321$
513537813	$9*((-8+7)^{\wedge}6*(54*3^{\wedge}2-1))$	559600953	$9^{\wedge}8*(7+6)-5*4*321$
513537957	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54*3^{\wedge}2-1))$	559602858	$9^{\wedge}8*(7+6)-5*43*21$
513760370	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5*4)^{\wedge}3/2+1)$	559603971	$9^{\wedge}8*(7+6)-54*3*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
559604484	$9^8*(7+6) - (5+4)*321$	584480249	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+2) - 1$
559605208	$9^8*(7+6) - 5*(432+1)$	584480251	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+2)+1$
559605218	$9^8*(7+6) - 5*(432-1)$	584480421	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+21)$
559605591	$9^8*(7+6) - 54*(32+1)$	585421247	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3) - 21)$
559605699	$9^8*(7+6) - 54*(32-1)$	585421265	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3) - 21)$
559605744	$9^8*(7+6) - 543*(2+1)$	585421583	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+21)$
559605748	$9^8*(7+6) - 5*(4+321)$	585421601	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+21)$
559605788	$9^8*(7+6)+5*(4-321)$	588009653	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3) - 2^{\wedge}-1)$
559606077	$9^8*(7+6) - 54*(3+21)$	588009751	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$
559606176	$9^8*(7+6) - (54+3)*21$	588379447	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3/21)$
559606302	$9^8*(7+6) - (54-3)*21$	588379465	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3/21)$
559606365	$9^8*(7+6) - (5+43)*21$	590872674	$-98*((7-6*5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
559606401	$9^8*(7+6)+54*(3-21)$	591068399	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3) - 21)$
559606575	$9^8*(7+6)+(5-43)*21$	591068417	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3) - 21)$
559608171	$9^8*(7+6) - (5-43)*21$	591068735	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+21)$
559608345	$9^8*(7+6) - 54*(3-21)$	591068753	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+21)$
559608381	$9^8*(7+6)+(5+43)*21$	593774503	$98*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2-1)$
559608444	$9^8*(7+6)+(54-3)*21$	594542271	$9^{\wedge}-8*7*(6^{\wedge}5)^{\wedge}4-321$
559608570	$9^8*(7+6)+(54+3)*21$	595068570	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3*21))$
559608669	$9^8*(7+6)+54*(3+21)$	595068714	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3*21))$
559608958	$9^8*(7+6) - 5*(4-321)$	599539206	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+32) - 1)$
559608998	$9^8*(7+6)+5*(4+321)$	599539402	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+32)+1)$
559609002	$9^8*(7+6)+543*(2+1)$	601774537	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
559609047	$9^8*(7+6)+54*(32-1)$	601774563	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
559609155	$9^8*(7+6)+54*(32+1)$	601774707	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
559609528	$9^8*(7+6)+5*(432-1)$	601774733	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
559609538	$9^8*(7+6)+5*(432+1)$	602245133	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
559610262	$9^8*(7+6)+(5+4)*321$	602245159	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
559610775	$9^8*(7+6)+54*3*21$	602245303	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
559611888	$9^8*(7+6)+5*43*21$	602245329	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}(3+2) - 1)$
559613793	$9^8*(7+6)+5*4*321$	602480431	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
559807998	$9^8*(7+6)+5^{\wedge}4*321$	602480457	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
561337047	$9^8*7+(6*5)^{\wedge}4*321$	602480601	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
562087431	$9^8*(7*(6*(5+4)^{\wedge}-3+2) - 1)$	602480627	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
562914117	$9^8*(7+6)+54^{\wedge}3*21$	602653513	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)/6-5)^*4-3)*21$
565656383	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3-21)$	602653709	$((9^{\wedge}8+7)/6-5)^*4-3)*21$
565656401	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3-21)$	602654479	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)/6+5)^*4+3)*21$
566230535	$9*8*(-7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$	602654675	$((9^{\wedge}8+7)/6+5)^*4+3)*21$
566230537	$9*8*(-7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	602951027	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
566231543	$9*8*(7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$	602951053	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
566231545	$9*8*(7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	602951197	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
568703562	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6)^{\wedge}5*43)*21$	602951223	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
571303535	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3-21)$	603976887	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4-321)$
571303553	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3-21)$	603982665	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4+321)$
572832900	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(543-2) - 1)$	605186447	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3+21)$
572832918	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(543-2)+1)$	605186465	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3+21)$
572833044	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(543-2) - 1)$	605304007	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2) - 1)$
572833062	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(543-2)+1)$	605304203	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2)+1)$
573891750	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(543-2+1))$	606634112	$(9/8/(7*6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
573891894	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(543-2+1))$	610833599	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+21)$
574950564	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*543-2-1)$	610833617	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+21)$
574950582	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*543-2+1)$	612219346	$-98*7+(6*54)^{\wedge}(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
574950600	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*543+2-1)$	612220718	$98*7+(6*54)^{\wedge}(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
574950618	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*543+2+1)$	616833707	$98*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2+1)$
574950708	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*543-2-1)$	617421943	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32-1)$
574950726	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*543-2+1)$	617421961	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32-1)$
574950744	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*543+2-1)$	618363127	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32) - 1)$
574950762	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*543+2+1)$	618363143	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32)+1)$
576009432	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2-1))$	618363145	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32) - 1)$
576009576	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2-1))$	618363161	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32)+1)$
576108279	$9*((8*7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	618394112	$(9/8/(7*6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
576108297	$9*((8*7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3/2+1)$	619304327	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+21)$
577068264	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2) - 1)$	619304345	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+21)$
577068282	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2)+1)$	620010213	$(9+8)*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3-2) - 1)$
577068408	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2) - 1)$	620010247	$(9+8)*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3-2)+1)$
577068426	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2)+1)$	621281201	$(9*8+7)*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
578127114	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2+1))$	621281359	$(9*8+7)*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
578127258	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2+1))$	622010246	$(9+8)*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1)$
582244901	$98*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	622010280	$(9+8)*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1)$
584480043	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3) - 21)$	622597528	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
584480213	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3) - 2) - 1$	622597724	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3^{\wedge}2+1)$
584480215	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3) - 2)+1$	622598165	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
622598263	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3/2-1)$	658599047	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+2)-1$
622598459	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3/2+1)$	658599049	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+2)+1$
622598557	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3/2-1)$	658599155	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-2)-1$
622598753	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3/2+1)$	658599157	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-2)+1$
622598851	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	658599191	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+2)-1$
622599292	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	658599193	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+2)+1$
622599488	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	658599219	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+2+1)$
622638297	$9^{\wedge}8*7-65^{\wedge}4*(3-21)$	658599363	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+2+1)$
626833800	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32-1))$	660010873	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$
626833944	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32-1))$	660010907	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$
627892632	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32)-1)$	660486150	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(-3+2+1)$
627892650	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32)+1)$	661657878	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
627892776	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32)-1)$	661658074	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
627892794	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32)+1)$	661774986	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+2+1)$
628010345	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$	661893176	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
628010379	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1)$	661893372	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
628363309	$98^*7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2-1)$	661926816	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3/2+1))$
628951482	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32+1))$	661926960	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3/2+1))$
628951626	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32+1))$	664951887	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-2+1)$
633983516	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-32+1)$	664952031	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-2+1)$
634037406	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-32+1)$	664952057	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-2)-1$
634540554	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*((6-5-4)^{\wedge}-3+2)+1)$	664952059	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-2)+1$
636010477	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3-2)-1)$	664952093	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2)-1$
636010511	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3-2)+1)$	664952095	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2)+1$
636363369	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3-2+1))$	664952201	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-2)-1$
636363513	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3-2+1))$	664952203	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-2)+1$
638599968	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*321$	664952237	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2)-1$
639892813	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2)-1)$	664952239	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2)+1$
639893009	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2)+1)$	664952265	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2+1)$
640010509	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4+3-2-1)$	664952409	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2+1)$
640010543	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4+3-2+1)$	671088550	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
640010577	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4+3+2-1)$	671088730	$(9+8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
640010611	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4+3+2+1)$	672950993	$(-9+8/7^{\wedge}-6*5)^*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
641901453	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)*321$	672953567	$(9+8/7^{\wedge}-6*5)^*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
641961480	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*321$	676331331	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)^4*43-2+1)$
642005136	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*321$	676331709	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)^4*43+2+1)$
642016050	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*321$	677658167	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*5/4^{\wedge}-3*2)-1$
642059706	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*321$	677658169	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*5/4^{\wedge}-3*2)+1$
642119733	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)*321$	680244460	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2+1)$
642716415	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3-2+1))$	680246224	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2+1)$
642716559	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3-2+1))$	680246469	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$
643220757	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7)^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3-2+1)$	680246567	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$
644010609	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2)-1)$	680246812	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-2-1)$
644010643	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2)+1)$	680248576	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-2+1)$
644821356	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	680834691	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3+2+1))$
644992227	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7-6^{\wedge}-5^{\wedge}4+3)^2+1)$	680834835	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2+1))$
645291952	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2)-1$	682362895	$(-9+8/7^{\wedge}-6*5)^*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
645421218	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*321$	682365505	$(9+8/7^{\wedge}-6*5)^*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
645527250	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2)+1$	684193239	$9+87*6*5*(4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
645689340	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)^*(4*3+2+1)$	684195309	$-9+87*6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2-1)$
645697665	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*6*5)^*(4*3+2+1)$	684195327	$9+87*6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2-1)$
645703965	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*6*5)^*(4*3+2+1)$	684195762	$9+87*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
645712290	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)^*(4*3+2+1)$	684195918	$-9+87*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
645997846	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	684195936	$9+87*(6*5*4^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
646409403	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7+6^{\wedge}-5^{\wedge}4+3)^2+1)$	684196371	$9+87*6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2+1)$
647295138	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+65)/(4-3/2+1)$	684198441	$-9+87*6*5*(4^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
647540087	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3*2+1)$	684198459	$9+87*6*5*(4^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
647540105	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3*2+1)$	686011183	$(9+8)^*(-7+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
648180873	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6^{\wedge}-5/4^{\wedge}-3+2)+1)$	686011217	$(9+8)^*(-7+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
649983100	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+32+1)$	686128870	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
650038350	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+32+1)$	686129066	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
651422513	$98^*7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2+1)$	687153213	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7+6+5)^4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
654294576	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7/6)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2-1)$	687187737	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2+1))$
654328272	$(9+8^{\wedge}7/6)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2-1)$	687187881	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2+1))$
656391674	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7/6)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1)$	688746752	$-9*87+(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}-2-1$
656425478	$(9+8^{\wedge}7/6)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1)$	688746754	$-9*87+(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}-2+1$
657187265	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	688746849	$-98*7+(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}-2-1$
657187363	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	688746850	$-98*7+(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}-2+1$
658598841	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-2+1)$	688746851	$-98*7+(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}-2+1$
658598985	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-2+1)$	688747430	$-98-7+(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}-2-1$
658599011	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-2)-1$	688747431	$-98-7+(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}-2/1$
658599013	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-2)+1$	688747432	$-98-7+(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}-2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
688747439	$-9-87+(6/54^3)^{-2-1}$	749424228	$98*(7^6*5*(4+3^2)+1)$
688747441	$-9-87+(6/54^3)^{-2+1}$	751071207	$-9-8*7^6*(5-43)^*21$
688747444	$-98+7+(6/54^3)^{-2-1}$	751071225	$9-8*7^6*(5-43)^*21$
688747446	$-98+7+(6/54^3)^{-2+1}$	753317582	$((9^8*7-6)^*5-43)/2+1$
688747459	$9-87+(6/54^3)^{-2+1}$	753317612	$((9^8*7+6)^*5-43)/2+1$
688747613	$-9-87+(6/54^3)^{-2-1}$	753317623	$((9^8*7-6)^*5+43)/2-1$
688747626	$98-7+(6/54^3)^{-2-1}$	753317653	$((9^8*7+6)^*5+43)/2-1$
688747628	$98-7+(6/54^3)^{-2+1}$	755293419	$(9+(8-7^6*5)^*4)^*-321$
688747631	$9+87+(6/54^3)^{-2-1}$	755296299	$-9-(8-7^6*5)^*4*321$
688747633	$9+87+(6/54^3)^{-2+1}$	755296317	$9-(8-7^6*5)^*4*321$
688747640	$98+7+(6/54^3)^{-2-1}$	755299197	$(9-(8-7^6*5)^*4)^*321$
688747641	$98+7+(6/54^3)^{-2/1}$	755301123	$(-9-8+7^6*5^4)^*321$
688747642	$98+7+(6/54^3)^{-2+1}$	755304003	$-9-(8-7^6*5^4)^*321$
688748221	$98*7+(6/54^3)^{-2-1}$	755304021	$9-(8-7^6*5^4)^*321$
688748222	$98*7+(6/54^3)^{-2*1}$	755306259	$(-9+8+7^6*5^4)^*321$
688748223	$98*7+(6/54^3)^{-2+1}$	755306901	$(9-8+7^6*5^4)^*321$
688748318	$9*87+(6/54^3)^{-2-1}$	755309139	$-9+(8+7^6*5^4)^*321$
688748320	$9*87+(6/54^3)^{-2+1}$	755309157	$9+(8+7^6*5^4)^*321$
690094071	$9*(8^7*65/(4/3)^{2-1})$	755312037	$(9+8+7^6*5^4)^*321$
690094089	$9*(8^7*65/(4/3)^{2+1})$	755313963	$(-9+(8+7^6*5^4)^*4)^*321$
690341859	$9^8*((-7+6+5)^*4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	755316843	$-9+(8+7^6*5^4)^*4*321$
694599624	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4+32-1))$	755316861	$9+(8+7^6*5^4)^*4*321$
694599768	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4+32-1))$	755319741	$(9+(8+7^6*5^4)^*4)^*321$
695658456	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4+32-1))$	760921294	$98*((7^6-5)^*(4^3+2)-1)$
695658474	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4+32)+1)$	760921490	$98*((7^6-5)^*(4^3+2)+1)$
695658600	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4+32-1))$	760985974	$98*((7^6+5)^*(4^3+2)-1)$
695658618	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4+32)+1)$	760986170	$98*((7^6+5)^*(4^3+2)+1)$
696717306	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4+32+1))$	763155288	$(9^8-7^6*(5^4+3))^*21$
696717450	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4+32+1))$	765097893	$(9^8-7^6*5^4)^*21$
696954762	$(9^8-(76-5)^4)^*3)^*-21$	768868898	$(9/8*((7^6+5)/4-3)^{-2})^{\wedge}-1$
703305624	$-98*(7^6*(5-4^3-2)+1)$	769182642	$(9/8*((7^6+5)/4+3)^{-2})^{\wedge}-1$
703305820	$-98*(7^6*(5-4^3-2)-1)$	770699734	$-98*(7-6*5*(4^3^2-1))$
705295138	$(9/(-8+(7+6)^*5^{\wedge}(4^3)^*2))^{\wedge}-1$	770702086	$-98*(7-6*(5^4^3^2-1))$
714804846	$98*((7^6-5)^*(4^3-2)-1)$	770702576	$-98*(7-6*5^4^3^2+1)$
714805042	$98*((7^6-5)^*(4^3-2)+1)$	770702772	$-98*(7-6*5^4^3^2-1)$
714865606	$98*((7^6+5)^*(4^3-2)-1)$	770703262	$-98*(7-6*(5^4^3^2+1))$
714865802	$98*((7^6+5)^*(4^3-2)+1)$	770703458	$98*(7+6*(5^4^3^2-1))$
715864149	$(9^8-(7+65)^4)^*3)^*21$	770704144	$98*(7+6*5^4^3^2+1)$
717226641	$-9-(8+7)^6*(5^{\wedge}-4-3)^*21$	770705614	$-98*(7-6*5*(4^3^2+1))$
717226659	$9-(8+7)^6*(5^{\wedge}-4-3)^*21$	770706986	$98*(7+6*5*(4^3^2+1))$
717992109	$9+(8+7)^6*(5^{\wedge}-4+3)^*21$	770799393	$(-9+8*7^6/5)^*(4^3)^2-1$
719710380	$-98*(7^6+5^4)^3)^*(2+1)$	770873103	$(9+8*7^6/5)^*(4^3)^2-1$
724354083	$9^8*((76/54^3)^2-1)$	772483236	$98*(7^6*(5+4^3-2)-1)$
726099374	$(9^8-(76-5)^4)^3)^*21$	772483432	$98*(7^6*(5+4^3-2)+1)$
727638906	$-9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)+5^{\wedge}(4^3)^*(2+1)$	773985978	$(9^8-76*5^4)^*(-3+21)$
729742047	$9^8*7+65^4)^*(3+21)$	774722880	$9^8*(7+(6-(5+4)^{-3})^2-1)$
732068830	$-98-(7^6-(5^4)^3)^*(2+1)$	774800154	$(9^8-7^6*5^4)^*(-3+21)$
732069026	$98-(7^6-(5^4)^3)^*(2+1)$	774808218	$(9^8-7^6*5^4)^*(-3+21)$
732362826	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)+5^{\wedge}(4^3)^*(2+1)$	774813618	$(9^8-76*5^4)^*(-3+21)$
732420990	$-9-876+(5^4)^3)^*(2+1)$	774828342	$(9^8-(7+6)^*5^4)^*(-3+21)$
732421008	$9-876+(5^4)^3)^*(2+1)$	774828666	$(9^8-76*(5+4))^*(-3+21)$
732422760	$9+876+(5^4)^3)^*(2+1)$	774832284	$(9^8-7*(6+5+4))^*(-3+21)$
732480924	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)+5^{\wedge}(4^3)^*(2+1)$	774833292	$(9^8-7*(6+5+4))^*(-3+21)$
732774724	$-98+(7^6+(5^4)^3)^*(2+1)$	774833418	$(9^8-7*(6+5+4))^*(-3+21)$
732774920	$98+(7^6+(5^4)^3)^*(2+1)$	774834930	$(9^8+7*(6-5+4))^*(-3+21)$
735306330	$9*(8+7^6*5^4)^*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	774835146	$(9^8-(76+5)^4)^*(-3+21)$
737204844	$9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)+5^{\wedge}(4^3)^*(2+1)$	774835794	$(9^8-(7+65)^4)^*(-3+21)$
737861110	$98*((7^6-5)^4)^3-21)$	774835866	$(9^8-(76-5)^4)^*(-3+21)$
737862874	$98*((7^6-5)^4)^3-2-1)$	774836802	$(9^8+(7-65)^4)^*(-3+21)$
737863070	$98*((7^6-5)^4)^3-2+1)$	774839268	$(9^8-76*5/4)^*(-3+21)$
737863119	$98*((7^6-5)^4)^3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	774839603	$((9^8-76)^*(5+4)^{-3})^2-1$
737863217	$98*((7^6-5)^4)^3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	774839615	$((9^8-76)^*(5+4)^3)^*2-1$
737863266	$98*((7^6-5)^4)^3+2-1)$	774839617	$((9^8-76)^*(5+4)^3)^*2+1$
737863462	$98*((7^6-5)^4)^3+2+1)$	774839694	$9^8*(7+6+5)^{-4}*321$
737865226	$98*((7^6-5)^4)^3+21)$	774839844	$(9^8-7/6*5^4)^*(-3+21)$
737923830	$98*((7^6+5)^4)^3-21)$	774840075	$9^8*(7+6+5)^{-4}*321$
737925839	$98*((7^6+5)^4)^3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	774841881	$9^8*(7+6+5)+43*21$
737925937	$98*((7^6+5)^4)^3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	774842112	$(9^8+7/6*5^4)^*(-3+21)$
737925986	$98*((7^6+5)^4)^3+2-1)$	774842262	$9^8*(7+6+5)+4*321$
737926182	$98*((7^6+5)^4)^3+2+1)$	774842351	$((9^8+76)^*(5+4)^3)^*2-1$
737927946	$98*((7^6+5)^4)^3+21)$	774842688	$(9^8+76*5/4)^*(-3+21)$
749424032	$98*(7^6*5*(4+3^2)-1)$	774845154	$(9^8-(7-65)^4)^*(-3+21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
774846090	$(9^8 + (76-5)^4)^* (-3+21)$	844955046	$-9^*(8+7^8*(5-43)^*21)$
774846162	$(9^8 + (7+65)^4)^* (-3+21)$	844955190	$9^*(8-7^8*(5-43)^*21)$
774846810	$(9^8 + (76+5)^4)^* (-3+21)$	844956630	$9^*(8-7^8*(5-43))^*21$
774847026	$(9^8 - 7^*(6-54))^* (-3+21)$	845190407	$-9-8^*7^8*(5-43^*21)$
774848538	$(9^8 + 7^*(6+54))^* (-3+21)$	845190425	$9-8^*7^8*(5-43^*21)$
774848664	$(9^8 + 7^*(65-4))^* (-3+21)$	849860067	$(-9+8^*(7^8-5)^*43)^*21$
774849672	$(9^8 + 7^*(65+4))^* (-3+21)$	849860445	$(9+8^*(7^8-5)^*43)^*21$
774853290	$(9^8 + 76^*(5+4))^* (-3+21)$	849932307	$(-9+8^*(7^8+5)^*43)^*21$
774853614	$(9^8 + (7+6)^*54)^* (-3+21)$	849932685	$(9+8^*(7^8+5)^*43)^*21$
774868338	$(9^8 + 76^*5^4)^* (-3+21)$	854014074	$(-9-8)^*(7^8+5)^*43+1)$
774873738	$(9^8 + 7^*65^4)^* (-3+21)$	854014108	$(-9-8)^*(7^8+5)^*43-1)$
774881802	$(9^8 + 7^*6^*54)^* (-3+21)$	854296632	$9^8((8+7)/6)^*(5^4*3)^{2-1}$
774959076	$9^8*(7+(6+(5+4)^{-3})^{2-1})$	854297118	$9^8((8+7)/6)^*(5^4*3)^{2+1}$
775115649	$9^8-(7^8-5^4(4^3))^*(2+1)$	854602327	$-9+8^*7^8*(5+43^*21)$
775695978	$(9^8 + 76^*5^4)^* (-3+21)$	854602345	$9+8^*7^8*(5+43^*21)$
775821543	$9^8+(7^8+5^4(4^3))^*(2+1)$	854696422	$9^8*7+65^4*(32-1)$
777599757	$9^8((8+7)/6)^*(5^4)^{(3+2)-1}$	854829045	$(9^8-7^*6^5*43)^*21$
777600243	$9^8((8+7)/6)^*(5^4)^{(3+2)+1}$	855690318	$(9^8-7^*(65+4)^3)^*21$
777979062	$(9^8-7^8*(54-3))^*21$	859509819	$(9^8-7^8*54/3)^*21$
779026717	$(9^8-(7+65^4)/3)^*21$	860816322	$9^8*(7+(6-(5+4)^{-3})^{2+1})$
779026815	$(9^8+(7-65^4)/3)^*21$	861052518	$9^8*(7+(6+(5+4)^{-3})^{2+1})$
785390949	$(9^8-7^8*(5+43))^*21$	861977588	$(9+8)^*(7^8-5)^*(432-1)$
789071787	$(9^8-(7+65)^4*3)^*-21$	862050858	$(9+8)^*(7^8+5)^*(432-1)$
790590519	$-9-(8-7^8*5)^4*3^*21$	863977519	$(9+8)^*(7^8-5)^*432-1)$
790590537	$9-(8-7^8*5)^4*3^*21$	863977553	$(9+8)^*(7^8+5)^*432+1)$
790592222	$(-98+7^8*5^4*3)^*21$	864050959	$(9+8)^*(7^8+5)^*432-1)$
790601103	$-9-(8-7^8*5^4*3)^*21$	864050993	$(9+8)^*(7^8+5)^*432+1)$
790601121	$9-(8-7^8*5^4*3)^*21$	864310633	$((9+8)/(7+6^8/5^4)^3*21)^{-1}$
790601182	$-98+7^8*5^4*3^*21$	865006823	$-98+((7^8-5)/4)^{(3-2+1)}$
790601378	$98+7^8*5^4*3^*21$	865006848	$9^*(-8+((7^8-5)/4/3)^2)-1$
790601439	$-9+(8+7^8*5^4*3)^*21$	865006850	$9^*(-8+((7^8-5)/4/3)^2)+1$
790601457	$9+(8+7^8*5^4*3)^*21$	865006992	$9^*(8+((7^8-5)/4/3)^2)-1$
790603338	$(98+7^8*5^4*3)^*21$	865006994	$9^*(8+((7^8-5)/4/3)^2)+1$
790612023	$-9+(8+7^8*5^4)^*4^3*21$	865007019	$98+((7^8-5)/4)^{(3-2+1)}$
790612041	$9+(8+7^8*5^4)^*4^3*21$	865977484	$(9+8)^*(7^8-5)^*(432+1)$
795540480	$98^*(7^8*(5+4^3)-21)$	866051094	$(9+8)^*(7^8+5)^*(432+1)$
795542244	$98^*(7^8*(5+4^3)-2-1)$	870614934	$(9^8-7^*(65-4)^3)^*21$
795542440	$98^*(7^8*(5+4^3)-2+1)$	872229141	$(9^8-7^*(6+54)^3)^*21$
795542489	$98^*(7^8*(5+4^3)-2^2-1)$	874014404	$(9+8)^*(7^8*(5+432)-1)$
795542587	$98^*(7^8*(5+4^3)+2^2-1)$	874014438	$(9+8)^*(7^8*(5+432)+1)$
795542636	$98^*(7^8*(5+4^3)+2-1)$	876249654	$-98^*(7^8*(5-43)^*2+1)$
795542832	$98^*(7^8*(5+4^3)+2+1)$	876249850	$-98^*(7^8*(5-43)^*2-1)$
795544596	$98^*(7^8*(5+4^3)+21)$	880648200	$(9^8-7^8*54)^*(3+21)$
796914729	$9+8^*76^*5^4(4^3*2-1)$	882448453	$(9^8-7^*65)^*(43/2-1)$
796917143	$-9+8^*76^*(5^4*3^2-1)$	882467108	$(9^8+7^*65)^*(43/2-1)$
796917161	$9+8^*76^*(5^4*3^2-1)$	883727334	$9^8*((-7^8/54)^3+21)$
796917759	$-9+8^*(76^*5^4*3^2+1)$	885976266	$(9^8-(76^5/4)^3)^*21$
796917761	$9+8^*(76^*5^4*3^2-1)$	887724117	$(9^8+7^*(6-54)^3)^*21$
796917777	$9+8^*(76^*5^4*3^2+1)$	889195806	$(9^8+7^8*54)^*(3-2+1)$
796918377	$9+8^*76^*(5^4*3^2+1)$	889418313	$9^*(8/7^8-6^5-43)^*21$
796920791	$-9+8^*76^*5^4(4^3*2+1)$	890367623	$-9+8^*7^8*(5^4+321)$
796920809	$9+8^*76^*5^4(4^3*2+1)$	890367641	$9+8^*7^8*(5^4+321)$
797739579	$(9^8-(7^8+5)^*43)^*21$	890397672	$9^8*7+65^4*(32+1)$
797748609	$(9^8-(7^8-5)^*43)^*21$	891213141	$(9^8-76^*(5^4)^3)^*21$
805133115	$9^8*((-7+6/54)/3+21)$	896528988	$-9^*(8-76^*5^4(4^3*2-1))$
806727438	$9^8*(7/-6+5)^*(4-3^2-2+1)$	896531724	$-9^*(8-76^*(5^4*3^2-1))$
810097239	$(9^8+7^8*(5-43))^*21$	896531868	$9^*(8+76^*(5^4*3^2-1))$
810447525	$9^8*((76/54^3)^2+1)$	896532399	$-9^*(8-76^*5^4*3^2+1)$
811510407	$9^8*(7^8-5^4/3^2(2+1))$	896532417	$-9^*(8-76^*5^4*3^2-1)$
816293382	$(9/(8^7+6^8/5^4)^3-2)^{-1}$	896532561	$9^*(8+76^*5^4*3^2+1)$
817873164	$(9^8-765)^*(4^*(3+2)-1)$	896533092	$-9^*(8-76^*(5^4*3^2+1))$
817883709	$(9^8-7^8*5^4)^*(4^*(3+2)-1)$	896535828	$-9^*(8-76^*5^4(4^3*2+1))$
817887378	$9^8*(-7+6^5-4)-321$	896535972	$9^*(8+76^*5^4(4^3*2+1))$
817888020	$9^8*(-7+6^5-4)+321$	896565852	$(9^8-(7^8+54)^3)^*21$
817891689	$(9^8+7^8*5^4)^*(4^*(3+2)-1)$	896572656	$(9^8-(7^8-54)^3)^*21$
817902234	$(9^8+765)^*(4^*(3+2)-1)$	898600447	$(9^8+7)^*(6/(5+43)+21)$
818601644	$98^*(7^8*(5+4^3+2)-1)$	898730154	$(9^8-(7/6^5)^3)^*21$
818601840	$98^*(7^8*(5+4^3+2)+1)$	899149902	$-98^*(7^*(6-5^4*3^2)-1)$
823065408	$(9^8-7^8/5^4-4)/-3^2(-2-1)$	899157938	$98^*(7^*(6+5^4*3^2)-1)$
823262328	$9^8*7+65^4*3^*21$	899158134	$98^*(7^*(6+5^4*3^2)+1)$
824765669	$(9^8-(7-65)^4/3)^*21$	900123273	$(9^8-7/6^5*4^3)^*21$
844953606	$-9^*(8+7^8*(5-43))^*21$	900988641	$(9^8-76^*5^4*3)^*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
902817657	$(9^8-76*(5+4)^3)^*21$	903974358	$(9^8-76*(5/4+3))^*21$
902831748	$(9^8-7*(6^5+43))^*21$	903974673	$(9^8-7*(6-5+43))^*21$
902844390	$(9^8-7*(6^5-43))^*21$	903974757	$(9^8-76*(5-4+3))^*21$
902978853	$(9^8-76*(5^4+3))^*21$	903974967	$(9^8+7*(6-5-43))^*21$
902988429	$(9^8-76*(5^4-3))^*21$	903975093	$(9^8-(7*6+54)^3)^*21$
903157220	$(9^8-(7^6+54)/3)^*21$	903975289	$(9^8-76*(5-4/3))^*21$
903157976	$(9^8-(7^6-54)/3)^*21$	903975786	$(9^8-(76+5+4)^3)^*21$
903369621	$(9^8-7*65*4^3)^*21$	903976227	$(9^8-(7+6)^*54/3)^*21$
903470421	$(9^8-76*5*4^3)^*21$	903976234	$(9^8-(76+5^4)/3)^*21$
903544293	$(-9+8*7^6*5/4^3)^*(2+1)$	903976437	$(9^8+7*(6+5-43))^*21$
903544347	$(9+8*7^6*5/4^3)^*(2+1)$	903976920	$(9^8-(76-5-4)^3)^*21$
903648641	$(9^8-76*5^4/3)^*21$	903977235	$(9^8+(7-65-4)^3)^*21$
903871017	$(9^8-76*(5+4^3))^*21$	903977340	$(9^8-(7+6^5)/43)^*21$
903872277	$(9^8-(76+5)^4)^3)^*21$	903977676	$(9^8-(7-6+54)^3)^*21$
903873978	$(9^8-7/(6/54)^3)^*21$	903977802	$(9^8+(7-6-54)^3)^*21$
903884373	$(9^8-(7+65)^4)^3)^*21$	903977949	$(9^8+76*(5-4-3))^*21$
903885717	$(9^8-(76-5)^4)^3)^*21$	903977984	$(9^8-(7*65-4)/3)^*21$
903886977	$(9^8+76*(5-4^3))^*21$	903978152	$(9^8-7*(65-4)/3)^*21$
903903189	$(9^8+(7-65)^4)^3)^*21$	903978201	$(9^8-7*(6+54)/3)^*21$
903911610	$(9^8-7*(6+5)^4)^3)^*21$	903978453	$(9^8-(76*5+4)/3)^*21$
903914256	$(9^8-7*65*(4+3))^*21$	903978509	$(9^8-(76*5-4)/3)^*21$
903922446	$(9^8-(7+6)^*5*43)^*21$	903978789	$(9^8+7*(6-54)/3)^*21$
903925281	$(9^8-76*5*(4+3))^*21$	903978824	$(9^8-(7+6*54)/3)^*21$
903930867	$(9^8-7*6*(54+3))^*21$	903978922	$(9^8+(7-6*54)/3)^*21$
903933072	$(9^8-7*(6*54+3))^*21$	903979153	$(9^8-(76-5)^4/3)^*21$
903933954	$(9^8-7*(6*54-3))^*21$	903979370	$(9^8+(7-65*4)/3)^*21$
903936159	$(9^8-7*6*(54-3))^*21$	903979517	$(9^8+(7-65)^4/3)^*21$
903936915	$(9^8-(7+6)^*54)^3)^*21$	903980001	$(9^8-76*5/(4+3))^*21$
903936978	$(9^8-(76+5^4)^3)^*21$	903980476	$(9^8-76*5/4/3)^*21$
903938049	$(9^8-76*(5+4)^3)^*21$	903980546	$(9^8-(76+5+4)/3)^*21$
903938805	$(9^8-7*6*(5+43))^*21$	903980665	$(9^8-(7+65-4)/3)^*21$
903942480	$(9^8-7*(65*4+3))^*21$	903980672	$(9^8-(76-5-4)/3)^*21$
903944433	$(9^8-76*(5*4+3))^*21$	903980693	$(9^8-(7+6/54)^3)^*21$
903946554	$(9^8+(76-5^4)^3)^*21$	903980749	$(9^8-(76-5*4)/3)^*21$
903947625	$(9^8+7*6*(5-43))^*21$	903980770	$(9^8+(7-6-54)/3)^*21$
903948654	$(9^8-7*(6+5*43))^*21$	903980928	$(9^8-(76-5)/(4+3))^*21$
903950418	$(9^8+7*(6-5*43))^*21$	903981354	$(9^8+(76-5)/(4+3))^*21$
903950712	$(9^8-7*(65+4)^3)^*21$	903981512	$(9^8-(7-6-54)/3)^*21$
903952224	$(9^8-(7*65+4)^3)^*21$	903981533	$(9^8+(76-5*4)/3)^*21$
903952728	$(9^8-(7*65-4)^3)^*21$	903981589	$(9^8+(7+6/54)^3)^*21$
903954009	$(9^8-76*(5*4-3))^*21$	903981610	$(9^8+(7+6+54)/3)^*21$
903954240	$(9^8-7*(65-4)^3)^*21$	903981617	$(9^8+(7+65-4)/3)^*21$
903954681	$(9^8-7*(6+54)^3)^*21$	903981736	$(9^8+(76+5+4)/3)^*21$
903956445	$(9^8-7*(6+54*3))^*21$	903981806	$(9^8+76*5/4/3)^*21$
903957453	$(9^8-(76*5-4)^3)^*21$	903982281	$(9^8+76*5/(4+3))^*21$
903958209	$(9^8+7*(6-54*3))^*21$	903982765	$(9^8-(7-65)^4/3)^*21$
903959973	$(9^8+7*(6-54)^3)^*21$	903982912	$(9^8-(7-65*4)/3)^*21$
903960288	$(9^8-(7+6*54)^3)^*21$	903983129	$(9^8+(76-5)^4/3)^*21$
903960729	$(9^8-(76+5)^4)^3)^*21$	903983360	$(9^8-(7-6*54)/3)^*21$
903961170	$(9^8+(7-6*54)^3)^*21$	903983458	$(9^8+(7+6*54)/3)^*21$
903961989	$(9^8-76*(5+4+3))^*21$	903983493	$(9^8-7*(6-54)/3)^*21$
903962178	$(9^8-7*(65+4^3))^*21$	903983773	$(9^8+(76*5-4)/3)^*21$
903962997	$(9^8-(7+65)^4)^3)^*21$	903983829	$(9^8+(76*5+4)/3)^*21$
903963249	$(9^8-(76-5)^4)^3)^*21$	903984081	$(9^8+7*(6+54)/3)^*21$
903964320	$(9^8-(7+65*4)^3)^*21$	903984130	$(9^8+7*(65-4)/3)^*21$
903965202	$(9^8+(7-65*4)^3)^*21$	903984298	$(9^8+(7*65-4)/3)^*21$
903965580	$(9^8-(7+6)^*(54+3))^*21$	903984333	$(9^8-76*(5-4-3))^*21$
903966525	$(9^8+(7-65)^4)^3)^*21$	903984480	$(9^8-(7-6-54)^3)^*21$
903967218	$(9^8-(7+6)^*(54-3))^*21$	903984606	$(9^8+(7-6+54)^3)^*21$
903968037	$(9^8-(7+6)^*(5+43))^*21$	903984942	$(9^8+(7+6^5)/43)^*21$
903968401	$(9^8-7*65*4/3)^*21$	903985047	$(9^8-(7-65-4)^3)^*21$
903969234	$(9^8-(76+5)^*(4+3))^*21$	903985362	$(9^8+(76-5-4)^3)^*21$
903969969	$(9^8+76*(5-4*3))^*21$	903985845	$(9^8-7*(6+5-43))^*21$
903970410	$(9^8-7*(6*5+43))^*21$	903986048	$(9^8+(76+5^4)/3)^*21$
903970501	$(9^8-76*5*4/3)^*21$	903986055	$(9^8+(7+6)^*54/3)^*21$
903970704	$(9^8-(76-5)^*(4+3))^*21$	903986496	$(9^8+(76+5+4)^3)^*21$
903970767	$(9^8+(7+6)^*(5-43))^*21$	903986993	$(9^8+76*(5-4/3))^*21$
903971033	$(9^8-76*(5+4/3))^*21$	903987189	$(9^8+(7*6+54)^3)^*21$
903971390	$(9^8-7*(65+4/3))^*21$	903987315	$(9^8-7*(6-5-43))^*21$
903971782	$(9^8-7*(65-4/3))^*21$	903987525	$(9^8+76*(5-4+3))^*21$
903972615	$(9^8-7*(65-4-3))^*21$	903987609	$(9^8+7*(6-5+43))^*21$
903973203	$(9^8-7*(6+5+43))^*21$	903987924	$(9^8+76*(5/4+3))^*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
903989079	$(9^8+7*(6+5+43))^*21$	908053642	$9^8+((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$
903989667	$(9^8+7*(65-4-3))^*21$	908114580	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^{\wedge}3^*21$
903990500	$(9^8+7*(65-4/3))^*21$	909232128	$(9^8+(7/6*5^4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$
903990892	$(9^8+7*(65+4/3))^*21$	909362129	$(9^8+7)^*(6/(5+43)+21)$
903991249	$(9^8+76*(5+4/3))^*21$	910108223	$9*(8*(7+6*5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2-1$
903991515	$(9^8-(7+6)^*(5-43))^*21$	910108225	$9*(8*(7+6*5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2+1$
903991578	$(9^8+(76-5)*(4+3))^*21$	911389626	$(9^8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3)^*21$
903991781	$(9^8+76*5^4/3)^*21$	911396430	$(9^8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3)^*21$
903991872	$(9^8+7*(6*5+43))^*21$	914838462	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3-21)$
903992313	$(9^8-76*(5-4*3))^*21$	914838786	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3-21)$
903993048	$(9^8+(76+5)*(4+3))^*21$	915406839	$9*((8+76*5)^4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
903993881	$(9^8+7*65^4/3)^*21$	915406857	$9*((8+76*5)^4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
903994245	$(9^8+(7+6)^*(5+43))^*21$	916749141	$(9^8+76*(5^4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$
903995064	$(9^8+(7+6)^*(54-3))^*21$	920238165	$(9^8-7*(6-54)^{\wedge}3)^*21$
903995757	$(9^8-(7-65)^4*3)^*21$	921986016	$(9^8+(76*5/4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$
903996702	$(9^8+(7+6)^*(54+3))^*21$	923113017	$9^8/(7*6-5*(4+3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$
903997080	$(9^8-(7-65^4)^*3)^*21$	924234948	$9^8*((7*6/54)^{\wedge}3+21)$
903997962	$(9^8+(7+65^4)^*3)^*21$	926301663	$9^8*7/6*(5*(4-3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
903999033	$(9^8+(76-5)^4*3)^*21$	935733141	$(9^8+7*(6+54)^{\wedge}3)^*21$
903999285	$(9^8+(7+65)^4*3)^*21$	935853961	$(9+8)^*7*(6*5^4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
904000104	$(9^8+7*(65+4^{\wedge}3))^*21$	935854063	$(9+8)^*(7*6*5^4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
904000293	$(9^8+76*(5+4+3))^*21$	935854097	$(9+8)^*(7*6*5^4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
904001112	$(9^8-(7-6*54)^*3)^*21$	935854199	$(9+8)^*7*(6*5^4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
904001553	$(9^8+(76+5)^4*3)^*21$	937347348	$(9^8+7*(65-4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$
904001994	$(9^8+(7+6*54)^*3)^*21$	938721273	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3-21)$
904002309	$(9^8-7*(6-54)^*3)^*21$	938721469	$98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3-21)$
904004073	$(9^8-7*(6-54*3))^*21$	940838955	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
904004829	$(9^8+(76*5-4)^*3)^*21$	940838981	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
904005837	$(9^8+7*(6+54*3))^*21$	940839125	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
904007601	$(9^8+7*(6+54)^*3)^*21$	940839151	$98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
904008042	$(9^8+7*(65-4)^*3)^*21$	941074253	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
904008273	$(9^8+76*(5^4-3))^*21$	941074279	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
904009554	$(9^8+(7*65-4)^*3)^*21$	941074423	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
904010058	$(9^8+(7*65+4)^*3)^*21$	941074449	$98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
904011570	$(9^8+7*(65+4)^*3)^*21$	941191881	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^4)^{\wedge}3-21$
904011864	$(9^8-7*(6-5*43))^*21$	941191923	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^4)^{\wedge}3+21$
904013628	$(9^8+7*(6+5*43))^*21$	941192077	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^4)^{\wedge}3-21$
904014657	$(9^8-7*6*(5-43))^*21$	941192119	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^4)^{\wedge}3+21$
904015728	$(9^8-(76-5^4)^*3)^*21$	941309551	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
904017849	$(9^8+76*(5^4+3))^*21$	941309577	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
904019802	$(9^8+7*(65^4+3))^*21$	941309721	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
904023477	$(9^8+7*6*(5+43))^*21$	941309747	$98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
904024233	$(9^8+76*(5+4)^*3)^*21$	941544849	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
904025304	$(9^8+(76+5^4)^*3)^*21$	941544875	$-9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
904025367	$(9^8+(7+6)*5^4*3)^*21$	941545019	$9*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
904026123	$(9^8+7*6*(54-3))^*21$	941545045	$98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
904028328	$(9^8+7*(6*54-3))^*21$	943662531	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3+21)$
904029210	$(9^8+7*(6*54+3))^*21$	943662727	$98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^4)^{\wedge}3+21)$
904031415	$(9^8+7*6*(54+3))^*21$	947027621	$((9^8-7)^*(6+5)-43)^*2-1$
904037001	$(9^8+76*5*(4+3))^*21$	947027793	$((9^8-7)^*(6+5)+43)^*2-1$
904039836	$(9^8+(7+6)*5^4*3)^*21$	947027795	$((9^8-7)^*(6+5)+43)^*2+1$
904048026	$(9^8+7*65*(4+3))^*21$	947028101	$((9^8+7)^*(6+5)+43)^*2-1$
904050672	$(9^8+7*(6+5)^4*3)^*21$	948452463	$(9^8+7^{\wedge}6*54/3)^*21$
904059093	$(9^8-(7-65)^4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$	950534242	$98*((7*6-5)^4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
904075305	$(9^8-76*(5-4^{\wedge}3))^*21$	950839146	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43*21))$
904076565	$(9^8+(76-5)^4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$	950839290	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-43*21))$
904077909	$(9^8+(7+65)^4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$	952271964	$(9^8+7*(65+4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$
904088304	$(9^8+7/(6/54)^{\wedge}3)^*21$	953133237	$(9^8+7*6^{\wedge}5*43)^*21$
904090005	$(9^8+(76+5)^4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$	954200529	$9+8*7*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
904091265	$(9^8+76*(5+4^{\wedge}3))^*21$	954204113	$9+8*7*(65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
904313641	$(9^8+76*5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$	954204159	$-9+8*(7*65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
904491861	$(9^8+76*5^4*3)^*21$	954204161	$9+8*(7*65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
904592661	$(9^8+7*65^4*3)^*21$	954204177	$9+8*(7*65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
904804306	$(9^8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)/3)^*21$	954207791	$-9+8*7*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
904805062	$(9^8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)/3)^*21$	954207809	$9+8*7*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
904973853	$(9^8+76*(5^{\wedge}4-3))^*21$	956091276	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^4*3)^*21$
904983429	$(9^8+76*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^*21$	956092716	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^4*3*21)$
905117892	$(9^8+7*(6^{\wedge}5-43))^*21$	956092860	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^4*3*21)$
905130534	$(9^8+7*(6^{\wedge}5+43))^*21$	956094300	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^4*3)^*21$
905144625	$(9^8+76*(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$	956172546	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^4*3)^*21$
906973641	$(9^8+76*5^{\wedge}4*3)^*21$	956173986	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^4*3*21)$
907839009	$(9^8+7/6*54^{\wedge}3)^*21$	956174130	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^4*3*21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
956175570	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43)^*21$	1033129080	$(9^{\wedge}8+(76+5)^*4)^*(3+21)$
961427556	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43^*21))$	1033129368	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*(6-54))^*(3+21)$
961427700	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43^*21))$	1033131384	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*(6+54))^*(3+21)$
968540985	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*65)^*(43/2+1)$	1033131552	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*(65-4))^*(3+21)$
968561460	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*65)^*(43/2+1)$	1033132896	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*(65+4))^*(3+21)$
976563109	$9+8*(76+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	1033137720	$(9^{\wedge}8+76*(5+4))^*(3+21)$
976563125	$9+8*(76+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/2+1)$	1033138152	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7+6)^*54)^*(3+21)$
983196613	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7-65)^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$	1033157784	$(9^{\wedge}8+76^*5^*4)^*(3+21)$
983885774	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	1033164984	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*65^*4)^*(3+21)$
984121072	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	1033175736	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6^*54)^*(3+21)$
984356370	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3+2-1)$	1034261304	$(9^{\wedge}8+76^*5^{\wedge}4)^*(3+21)$
984591668	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3+2+1)$	1034715627	$9^{\wedge}8*((7-6+5)^*4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
990073299	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+6^*5)-4^*321$	1037657124	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4)^*(3-21)$
990073680	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+6^*5)-43^*21$	1037671236	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4)^*(3-21)$
990075486	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+6^*5)+43^*21$	1042864389	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6^*54^{\wedge}3)^*21$
990075867	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+6^*5)+4^*321$	1044806994	$(9^{\wedge}8+76^*(54+3))^*21$
992436444	$-98+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$	1049193684	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+43^*2)-1)$
992436445	$-98+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}(3+2)^{\wedge}1$	1049193880	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+43^*2)+1)$
992436446	$-98+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	1054605321	$-9*(8-7^*65)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
992436640	$98+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}(3+2)-1$	1055441826	$9^{\wedge}8*(7+(6/5/4)^{\wedge}-3/2-1)$
992436641	$98+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}(3+2)^{\wedge}1$	1056964589	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*(4+3)-2)-1$
992436642	$98+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}(3+2)+1$	1056964591	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*(4+3)-2)+1$
997002990	$-9-(876-5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1056964625	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*(4+3)+2)-1$
997003008	$9-(876-5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1056964627	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*(4+3)+2)+1$
997865043	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))^*21$	1059534081	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6^*5*(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
1001663514	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+321))$	1067310216	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*21$
1001663658	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+321))$	1067311035	$(-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6^*54-3))^*21$
1002829167	$9^{\wedge}8*((7-6/54)/3+21)$	1067311215	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6^*54-3)^*21$
1008016641	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)^*21$	1067311233	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6^*54-3)^*21$
1010213673	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43)^*21$	1067311413	$(9+8*(7^{\wedge}6^*54-3))^*21$
1010222703	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43)^*21$	1067312043	$(-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6^*54+3))^*21$
1010800782	$9^{\wedge}8*(7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3+2+1)$	1067312223	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6^*54+3)^*21$
1015583751	$9^{\wedge}8*7+(6^*54)^{\wedge}3^*21$	1067312241	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6^*54+3)^*21$
1016487262	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^*5*(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1067312421	$(9+8*(7^{\wedge}6^*54+3))^*21$
1016487458	$98+7^{\wedge}6^*5*(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	1067313240	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*21$
1021193311	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(543^*2-1)$	1071378441	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5))^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1021193329	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(543^*2-1)$	1071386615	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5))^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1022571333	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*21$	1073475513	$-9*(8-7^*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
1023075713	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(543^*2+1)$	1073479545	$-9*(8-7*(65^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
1026289071	$-9*(87*(6-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	1073479599	$-9*(8-7^*65^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1026298449	$9*(87*(6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	1073479617	$-9*(8-7^*65^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1026298467	$9*(87*(6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	1073479761	$9*(8+7^*65^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1028935467	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7-65^{\wedge}4)/3)^*21$	1073483703	$-9*(8-7^*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
1028935565	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7+65^{\wedge}4)/3)^*21$	1073483847	$9*(8+7^*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
1029192156	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*54)^*(3-21)$	1075400388	$9^{\wedge}8*((7+6)^*((-5-4)^{\wedge}-3+2)-1)$
1029194748	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*54)^*(3-21)$	1076049927	$9^{\wedge}8*((7+6-(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)^*2-1)$
1029983220	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*21$	1076097015	$(9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5))^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1031981304	$(9^{\wedge}8-76^*5^{\wedge}4)^*(3+21)$	1076105225	$(9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5))^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1033066872	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^*54)^*(3+21)$	1076148900	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)^*(4^*3^*2+1)$
1033077624	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*65^*4)^*(3+21)$	1076162775	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6^*5)^*(4^*3^*2+1)$
1033084824	$(9^{\wedge}8-76^*5^*4)^*(3+21)$	1076166100	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(6+5))^*(4^*3^*2+1)$
1033104456	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7+6)^*54)^*(3+21)$	1076167815	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*6/5)^*(4^*3^*2+1)$
1033104888	$(9^{\wedge}8-76*(5+4))^*(3+21)$	1076168235	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6/5)^*(4^*3^*2+1)$
1033109712	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(65+4))^*(3+21)$	1076169950	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*(6+5))^*(4^*3^*2+1)$
1033111056	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(65-4))^*(3+21)$	1076173275	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*6^*5)^*(4^*3^*2+1)$
1033111224	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(6+54))^*(3+21)$	1076187150	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)^*(4^*3^*2+1)$
1033113240	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*(6-54))^*(3+21)$	1076286123	$9^{\wedge}8*((7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)^*2-1)$
1033113528	$(9^{\wedge}8-(76+5)^*4)^*(3+21)$	1076935662	$9^{\wedge}8*((7+6)^*((5+4)^{\wedge}-3+2)-1)$
1033114392	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7+65)^*4)^*(3+21)$	1078963438	$-98*7*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
1033114488	$(9^{\wedge}8-(76-5)^*4)^*(3+21)$	1078964026	$-98*(7^*6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
1033115736	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7-65)^*4)^*(3+21)$	1078964222	$-98*(7^*6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
1033118574	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*65/4)^*(3+21)$	1078964810	$-98*7*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
1033119024	$(9^{\wedge}8-76^*5/4)^*(3+21)$	1079004598	$98*7*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
1033120818	$(9^{\wedge}8-(76+5)/4)^*(3+21)$	1079005382	$98*(7^*6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
1033120878	$(9^{\wedge}8-(76-5)/4)^*(3+21)$	1081862908	$(9^{\wedge}8+(76-5)^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$
1033121730	$(9^{\wedge}8+(76-5)/4)^*(3+21)$	1082017836	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(543-2)-1)$
1033121790	$(9^{\wedge}8+(76+5)/4)^*(3+21)$	1082017870	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(543-2)+1)$
1033123584	$(9^{\wedge}8+76^*5/4)^*(3+21)$	1084253111	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}(6/5)^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$
1033124034	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*65/4)^*(3+21)$	1084253113	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}(6/5)^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))+1$
1033126872	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7-65)^*4)^*(3+21)$	1084253255	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}(6/5)^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))-1$
1033128120	$(9^{\wedge}8+(76-5)^*4)^*(3+21)$	1084253257	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}(6/5)^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2))+1$
1033128216	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7+65)^*4)^*(3+21)$	1086017868	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*543-2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1086017884	$(9+8)^*(7^6*543-2)-1$	1140505839	$9^8*7+654^3*(2+1)$
1086017885	$(9+8)^*(7^6*543-2)^{\wedge}1$	1141535268	$9^8*(7+(6/5/4)^{\wedge}-3/2+1)$
1086017886	$(9+8)^*(7^6*543-2)+1$	1145827053	$(-9+876^5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
1086017902	$(9+8)^*(7^6*543-2+1)$	1145835795	$(-9+876^5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
1086017936	$(9+8)^*(7^6*543+2-1)$	1148186331	$-9+876^5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
1086017952	$(9+8)^*(7^6*543+2)-1$	1148186349	$9+876^5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
1086017953	$(9+8)^*(7^6*543+2)^{\wedge}1$	1148189835	$-9+876^5*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
1086017954	$(9+8)^*(7^6*543+2)+1$	1148189853	$9+876^5*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
1086017970	$(9+8)^*(7^6*543+2+1)$	1148191587	$-9+876^5*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
1086895656	$(-98+7^6*5)^*(43^{\wedge}2-1)$	1148191605	$9+876^5*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
1087061967	$-9-(8-7^6*5)^*(43^{\wedge}2-1)$	1148195091	$-9+876^5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
1087061985	$9-(8-7^6*5)^*(43^{\wedge}2-1)$	1148195109	$9+876^5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
1087076662	$-98+7^6*5*(43^{\wedge}2-1)$	1148842413	$9^*(-8+7^6*(543^*2-1))$
1087076858	$98+7^6*5*(43^{\wedge}2-1)$	1148842557	$9^*(8+7^6*(543^*2-1))$
1087091535	$-9+(8+7^6*5)^*(43^{\wedge}2-1)$	1149901173	$9^*((-8+7^6*543)^*2-1)$
1087091553	$9+(8+7^6*5)^*(43^{\wedge}2-1)$	1149901191	$9^*((-8+7^6*543)^*2+1)$
1087257864	$(98+7^6*5)^*(43^{\wedge}2-1)$	1149901245	$9^*(-8+7^6*543^*2-1)$
1087547258	$-98+7^6*5*(5^*43^{\wedge}2-1)$	1149901263	$9^*(-8+7^6*543^*2+1)$
1087547454	$98+7^6*5*(5^*43^{\wedge}2-1)$	1149901389	$9^*(8+7^6*543^*2-1)$
1087782556	$-98+7^6*5*(5^*43^{\wedge}2+1)$	1149901407	$9^*(8+7^6*543^*2+1)$
1087782752	$98+7^6*5*(5^*43^{\wedge}2+1)$	1149901461	$9^*((8+7^6*543)^*2-1)$
1088071950	$(-98+7^6*5)^*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$	1149901479	$9^*((8+7^6*543)^*2+1)$
1088238441	$-9-(8-7^6*5)^*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$	1150545627	$(9+876^5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
1088238459	$9-(8-7^6*5)^*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$	1150554405	$(9+876^5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
1088253152	$-98+7^6*5*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$	1150960095	$9^*(-8+7^6*(543^*2+1))$
1088253348	$98+7^6*5*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$	1150960239	$9^*(8+7^6*(543^*2+1))$
1088268041	$-9+(8+7^6*5)^*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$	1152216387	$9^*((8^*7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21)$
1088268059	$9+(8+7^6*5)^*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$	1152216555	$9^*(8^*7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21$
1088434550	$(98+7^6*5)^*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$	1152216597	$9^*(8^*7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21$
1090017968	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(543+2)-1)$	1152216765	$9^*((8^*7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21)$
1090018002	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(543+2)+1)$	1156748112	$9^*((87+6^*5^4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
1092098133	$(9^8+(7+65)^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$	1156748130	$9^*((87+6^*5^4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
1092111255	$9^8*(-7+6^*5+(4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	1159982775	$(9+876^5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
1092354039	$9^*(8+7^6*5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$	1159986315	$(9+876^5)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
1092354057	$9^*((8+7^6*5)^*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$	1159988085	$(9+876^5)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
1092588058	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7/6)^*(5^{\wedge}4*(3+2)+1)$	1159991625	$(9+876^5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
1092644326	$(9+8^{\wedge}7/6)^*(5^{\wedge}4*(3+2)+1)$	1161493830	$9^8*((-7-6)^*(5+4)^{\wedge}3-2)+1$
1094713272	$-9^*8*((7-65)^*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$	1161848124	$9^8*(7^*(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$
1094713416	$-9^*8*((7-65)^*4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$	1162143369	$9^8*((7+6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$
1097072649	$9^*((87+6)^*5^*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$	1162249182	$(9^8-7^*65)^*(-4+32-1)$
1098632729	$-9^*(8+7/6-(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/2)-1$	1162251207	$(9^8-76^5)^*(-4+32-1)$
1098632731	$-9^*(8+7/6-(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/2)+1$	1162261429	$(9^8-76/54)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
1098632750	$-9^*(8-7/6-(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/2)-1$	1162261433	$((9^8-7/6)^*54-3)/2-1$
1098632752	$-9^*(8-7/6-(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/2)+1$	1162261501	$((9^8+7/6)^*54+3)/2+1$
1098632873	$9^*(8-7/6+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/2)-1$	1162261505	$(9^8+76/54)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
1098632875	$9^*(8-7/6+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/2)+1$	1162271727	$(9^8+76^5)^*(-4+32-1)$
1098632894	$9^*(8+7/6+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/2)-1$	1162273752	$(9^8+7^*65)^*(-4+32-1)$
1098632896	$9^*(8+7/6+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/2)+1$	1162379565	$9^8*((7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$
1106841694	$98^*(7^6*(5+43)^*2-1)$	1163029104	$9^8*((7+6)^*(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
1106841890	$98^*(7^6*(5+43)^*2+1)$	1166136879	$-9-8^*7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
1114431777	$9^8*(7^6/54^*32+1)$	1166136897	$9-8^*7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)^*21$
1119842364	$9^8*(8+7-6)+5^{\wedge}(4^*3)^*(2+1)$	1169890469	$(-9+8^*7^6)^*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2-1)$
1121513112	$9^*((87-6^*5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	1169912843	$(9+8^*7^6)^*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2-1)$
1121513130	$9^*((87-6^*5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	1171772835	$(-9+8^*7^6)^*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2+1)$
1124529156	$9^8/((7/6-5)^*4/3)^{\wedge}-2^{\wedge}1$	1171795245	$(9+8^*7^6)^*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2+1)$
1134017199	$9^*(-8+7^6*(54-3))^*21$	1173861719	$9^*(-8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$
1134018639	$9^*(-8+7^6*(54-3))^*21$	1173861721	$9^*(-8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$
1134018783	$9^*(8+7^6*(54-3))^*21$	1173861863	$9^*(8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$
1134020223	$9^*(8+7^6*(54-3))^*21$	1173861865	$9^*(8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$
1136389905	$(-9+876^5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$	1175131884	$(-9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3/2-1)$
1136393373	$(-9+876^5)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$	1175133741	$(9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3/2-1)$
1136395107	$(-9+876^5)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$	1176019306	$98^*(7^6*(54-3)^*2-1)$
1136398575	$(-9+876^5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$	1176019502	$98^*(7^6*(54-3)^*2+1)$
1137503925	$(9^8-7^6*54)^*(32-1)$	1176610353	$9^8*(7+(65-4)/3)-21$
1137645368	$9^*(-8+(7-6^*5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	1176610395	$9^8*(7+(65-4)/3)+21$
1137645370	$9^*(-8+(7-6^*5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	1178580311	$9^*(-8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$
1137645512	$9^*(8+(7-6^*5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	1178580313	$9^*(-8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$
1137645514	$9^*(8+(7-6^*5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	1178580455	$9^*(8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^2)-1$
1140480368	$9^*(-8+(7+6^*5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	1178580457	$9^*(8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^2)+1$
1140480370	$9^*(-8+(7+6^*5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	1181184665	$(-9+8^*7^6)^*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2-1)$
1140480512	$9^*(8+(7+6^*5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	1181207255	$(9+8^*7^6)^*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2-1)$
1140480514	$9^*(8+(7+6^*5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	1183067031	$(-9+8^*7^6)^*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1183089657	$(9+8*7^6)^*((5^4+3)^2+1)$	1248365929	$(9^8+76*5)^*(-4+32+1)$
1185594408	$(9^8+7^6*54)^*(3+21)$	1248368104	$(9^8+7^6*65)^*(-4+32+1)$
1197913116	$(-9+(8+7)^6)^*(5^4/3/2+1)$	1249734889	$(9+8)^*((7^6)^5/(4/3)^2-1)$
1197915009	$(9+(8+7)^6)^*(5^4/3/2+1)$	1249734923	$(9+8)^*((7^6)^5/(4/3)^2+1)$
1200723615	$9*(-8+7^6*54-3)^*21$	1249949232	$9^8*(-7+(6/5/4)^{-3}-2+1)$
1200724749	$9*(-8+7^6*54+3)^*21$	1252020641	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5^4+3-2)-1)$
1200725055	$9*(-8+(7^6*54-3)^*21)$	1252020675	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5^4+3-2)+1)$
1200725199	$9*(8+(7^6*54-3)^*21)$	1256020673	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5^4+3)-2-1)$
1200726189	$9*(-8+(7^6*54+3)^*21)$	1256020707	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5^4+3)-2+1)$
1200726333	$9*(8+(7^6*54+3)^*21)$	1256020741	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5^4+3)+2-1)$
1200726639	$9*(8+7^6*54-3)^*21$	1256020775	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5^4+3)+2+1)$
1200727773	$9*(8+7^6*54+3)^*21$	1260020773	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5^4+3+2)-1)$
1204723456	$(-9+8*7^6*5)^*4^{(3+2-1)}$	1260020807	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5^4+3+2)+1)$
1204728064	$(9+8*7^6*5)^*4^{(3+2-1)}$	1260256079	$-9-8*7^6*(5-4^3*21)$
1205249139	$9^8*(7-(6/54)^3+21)$	1260256097	$9-8*7^6*(5-4^3*21)$
1205367237	$9^8*(7+(6/54)^3+21)$	1262020806	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5^4+3^2)-1)$
1208436279	$(-9+8*(7^6-5)^4)^*321$	1262020840	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5^4+3^2)+1)$
1208439159	$-9+8*(7^6-5)^4*321$	1264908279	$-9+8*(7^6-5)^4*321$
1208439177	$9+8*(7^6-5)^4*321$	1264908297	$9+8*(7^6-5)^4*321$
1208442057	$(9+8*(7^6-5)^4)^*321$	1265015817	$9+8*(7^6+5)^4*321$
1208481219	$(-9+(8*7^6-5)^4)^*321$	1267431165	$9*(-8+7^6*(54+3))^*21$
1208494059	$(-9+(8*7^6+5)^4)^*321$	1267432605	$9*(-8+7^6*(54+3))^*21$
1208499837	$(9+(8*7^6+5)^4)^*321$	1267432749	$9*(8+7^6*(54+3))^*21$
1208538999	$(-9+8*(7^6+5)^4)^*321$	1267434189	$9*(8+7^6*(54+3))^*21$
1208541879	$-9+8*(7^6+5)^4*321$	1268020905	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5^4+3^2)-1)$
1208541897	$9+8*(7^6+5)^4*321$	1268020939	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5^4+3^2)+1)$
1208544777	$(9+8*(7^6+5)^4)^*321$	1269667999	$-9+8*7^6*(5+4^3*21)$
1210476498	$98*(7^6*5-4^3)^*21$	1269668017	$9+8*7^6*(5+4^3*21)$
1210593804	$98*(7^6*5-4-3)^*21$	1272971237	$(-9-8^7*(6-5^4/3))^*(2+1)$
1210605466	$98*(7^6*5-4/3)^*21$	1272971291	$(9-8^7*(6-5^4/3))^*(2+1)$
1210606152	$98*(7^6*5-4+3)^*21$	1281835692	$9^8*(7*((6-5)^4+3^2-2)+1)$
1210610268	$98*(7^6*5+4-3)^*21$	1304223039	$(9^8+7^6*54^3)^*21$
1210610954	$98*(7^6*5+4/3)^*21$	1306525693	$(-9-8^7*(6-5^4/3))/(2+1)$
1210622616	$98*(7^6*5+4+3)^*21$	1306525699	$(9-8^7*(6-5^4/3))/(2+1)$
1210739922	$98*(7^6*5+4^3)^*21$	1311903927	$-9*(8+7^6*(5-4^3))^*21$
1210891275	$(9^8-7^6*54)^*(32+1)$	1311904071	$9*(8-7^6*(5-4^3))^*21$
1219756041	$9*((87^6-5)^4*3^2+1)$	1314374530	$98*(7^6*(54+3)^2-1)$
1219784616	$(-9+8*7^6*54)^*(3+21)$	1314374726	$98*(7^6*(54+3))^*21$
1219785048	$(9+8*7^6*54)^*(3+21)$	1314914301	$(-9+8^7*(6+5^4/3))/(2+1)$
1226833425	$-9*(8*(7-65*4^3/2)-1)$	1314914307	$(9+8^7*(6+5^4/3))/(2+1)$
1226834415	$9*(8*(7+65*4^3/2)-1)$	1317198131	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4-3))^2-1$
1226834433	$9*(8*(7+65*4^3/2)+1)$	1317198133	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4-3))^2+1$
1227902613	$98*7^6*(5^4/2-1)$	1317198275	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4-3))^2-1$
1231528239	$-9*87*(6*(5-4^3/2)+1)$	1317198277	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4-3))^2+1$
1231529013	$9*(-87*6*(5-4^3/2)-1)$	1329065010	$(-9+87)*65*(4^3/2-1)$
1231529031	$9*(-87*6*(5-4^3/2)+1)$	1329070002	$(-9+87)*65*(4^3/2-1)$
1231529805	$-9*87*(6*(5-4^3/2)-1)$	1329070158	$(-9+87)*65*(4^3/2+1)$
1231575219	$9*87*(6*(5+4^3/2)-1)$	1329075150	$(-9+87)*65*(4^3/2+1)$
1231576011	$9*(87*6*(5+4^3/2)+1)$	1329665382	$9^8*(7-6/54+3+21)$
1232020311	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4-3^2)-1)$	1329904223	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4+3))^2-1$
1232020345	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4-3^2)+1)$	1329904225	$9*(-8+7^6*(5^4+3))^2+1$
1238020410	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4-3^2)-1)$	1329904367	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4+3))^2-1$
1238020444	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4-3^2)+1)$	1329904369	$9*(8+7^6*(5^4+3))^2+1$
1239258720	$(9^8+(7+6)^5*43)^*21$	1332975851	$(9^8-76*5^4)^*(32-1)$
1239432117	$98*(7^6*5^4/2-1)$	1334378043	$(9^8-7^6*5^4)^*(32-1)$
1239432313	$98*(7^6*5^4/2+1)$	1334391931	$(9^8-7^6*5^4)^*(32-1)$
1240020443	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4-3-2)-1)$	1334401231	$(9^8-76*5^4)^*(32-1)$
1240020477	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4-3-2)+1)$	1334426589	$(9^8-(7+6)^5*4)^*(32-1)$
1244020475	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4-3)-2-1)$	1334427147	$(9^8-76*(5+4))^*(32-1)$
1244020509	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4-3)-2+1)$	1334433378	$(9^8-7^6*(65+4))^*(32-1)$
1244020543	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4-3)+2-1)$	1334435114	$(9^8-7^6*(65+4))^*(32-1)$
1244020577	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4-3)+2+1)$	1334435331	$(9^8-7^6*(6+54))^*(32-1)$
1245196330	$98*((7^6*54-3)^2-1)$	1334437935	$(9^8+7^6*(6-54))^*(32-1)$
1245196526	$98*((7^6*54-3)^2+1)$	1334438307	$(9^8-(76+5)^4)^*(32-1)$
1245197506	$98*((7^6*54+3)^2-1)$	1334439423	$(9^8-(7+65)^4)^*(32-1)$
1245197702	$98*((7^6*54+3)^2+1)$	1334439547	$(9^8-(76-5)^4)^*(32-1)$
1247646402	$9^8/((-7+(6-(5+4)^{-3})^2)^{-1})$	1334441159	$(9^8+(7-65)^4)^*(32-1)$
1247941566	$9^8*(7*(6-(5+4)^{-3}-2)+1)$	1334445406	$(9^8-76*5/4)^*(32-1)$
1248020575	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4-3+2)-1)$	1334446398	$(9^8-7/6*54)^*(32-1)$
1248020609	$(9+8)*(7^6*(5^4-3+2)+1)$	1334450304	$(9^8+7/6*54)^*(32-1)$
1248341714	$(9^8-7^6*5)^*(-4+32+1)$	1334451296	$(9^8+76*5/4)^*(32-1)$
1248343889	$(9^8-76*5)^*(-4+32+1)$	1334455543	$(9^8-(7-65)^4)^*(32-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1334457155	$(9^8 + (76-5)^4)^*(32-1)$	1420534137	$(9^8 + (7-65)^4)^*(32+1)$
1334457279	$(9^8 + (7+65)^4)^*(32-1)$	1420538658	$(9^8 - 76^5/4)^*(32+1)$
1334458395	$(9^8 + (76+5)^4)^*(32-1)$	1420539714	$(9^8 - 7/6^5)^*(32+1)$
1334458767	$(9^8 - 7^*(6-54))^*(32-1)$	1420541472	$9^8*(7^6-5-4)-321$
1334461371	$(9^8 + 7^*(6+54))^*(32-1)$	1420542114	$9^8*(7^6-5-4)+321$
1334461588	$(9^8 + 7^*(65-4))^*(32-1)$	1420543872	$(9^8 + 7/6^5)^*(32+1)$
1334463324	$(9^8 + 7^*(65+4))^*(32-1)$	1420544928	$(9^8 + 76^5/4)^*(32+1)$
1334469555	$(9^8 + 76^*(5+4))^*(32-1)$	1420549449	$(9^8 - (7-65)^4)^*(32+1)$
1334470113	$(9^8 + (7+6)^5)^*(32-1)$	1420551165	$(9^8 + (76-5)^4)^*(32+1)$
1334495471	$(9^8 + 76^5)^*(32-1)$	1420551297	$(9^8 + (7+65)^4)^*(32+1)$
1334504771	$(9^8 + 7^6)^*(32-1)$	1420552485	$(9^8 + (76+5)^4)^*(32+1)$
1334518659	$(9^8 + 7^6)^*(32-1)$	1420552881	$(9^8 - 7^*(6-54))^*(32+1)$
1335920851	$(9^8 + 76^5)^*(32-1)$	1420555653	$(9^8 + 7^*(6+54))^*(32+1)$
1336042674	$9^8*(-7+(6/5/4)^{-3+2-1})$	1420555884	$(9^8 + 7^*(65-4))^*(32+1)$
1339843064	$98*7*((6-5+4)^3)^2-1$	1420557732	$(9^8 + 7^*(65+4))^*(32+1)$
1339843652	$98*7^*(6-5+4)^3)^2-1$	1420564365	$(9^8 + 76^*(5+4))^*(32+1)$
1339843848	$98*7^*(6-5+4)^3)^2+1$	1420564959	$(9^8 + (7+6)^5)^*(32+1)$
1339844436	$98*7^*((6-5+4)^3)^2+1$	1420591953	$(9^8 + 76^5)^*(32+1)$
1343225847	$-9*(8^7/(6/(5-432))+1)$	1420601853	$(9^8 + 7^6)^*(32+1)$
1343225865	$-9*(8^7/(6/(5-432))-1)$	1420616637	$(9^8 + 7^6)^*(32+1)$
1344014288	$9^8*(-7^6/54+32)-1$	1422109293	$(9^8 + 76^5)^*(32+1)$
1344014290	$9^8*(-7^6/54+32)+1$	1422655497	$9*((8^7-5)^4)^3)^2+1$
1346368695	$(-9+8^7(7+6-5)/4)^*321$	1423021752	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4)^3)^2+1$
1346374473	$(9+8^7(7+6-5)/4)^*321$	1423021896	$9*(8+(7^6-5)^4)^3)^2+1$
1348468709	$(-9+8^7(6+5+4/3))^*(2+1)$	1423142712	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4)^3)^2+1$
1348468763	$(9+8^7(6+5+4/3))^*(2+1)$	1425916422	$9^8*7+65^4)^3)^2+1$
1354257567	$-9*(8+7^6(5-4^3)^2)^2+1$	1428376437	$9*(-8+7^6(5+4^3)^2)^2+1$
1354257711	$9*(8-7^6(5-4^3)^2)^2+1$	1428376581	$9*(8+7^6(5+4^3)^2)^2+1$
1359470952	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4)^3)^2+1$	1434424536	$-9^8*(76^*(5-4^3)^2)^2+1$
1359493992	$9*(-8+(7^6-5)^4)^3)^2+1$	1434424599	$-9*(8^7(5-4^3)^2)^2+1$
1359494136	$9*(8+(7^6-5)^4)^3)^2+1$	1434424617	$-9*(8^7(5-4^3)^2)^2-1$
1359609552	$9*(-8+(7^6+5)^4)^3)^2+1$	1434424680	$-9^8*(76^*(5-4^3)^2)^2-1$
1359609696	$9*(8+(7^6+5)^4)^3)^2+1$	1434479256	$9^8*(76^*(5+4^3)^2)^2-1$
1359632736	$9*(8+(7^6+5)^4)^3)^2+1$	1434479337	$9*(8^7(5+4^3)^2)^2+1$
1360492938	$-98*(7^6(5-4^3)^2)^2+1$	1435166376	$(9^8+7^6(5^4)^3)^2+1$
1360493134	$-98*(7^6(5-4^3)^2)^2-1$	1456914688	$-9^8*7+(6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
1363062719	$-9/((8-7^6)^{-5}/(4/3+2))-1$	1474337772	$(9^8-7^6(5^4)^3)^2-1$
1363062721	$-9/((8-7^6)^{-5}/(4/3+2))+1$	1475726238	$98*((7^6-5)^4)^3)^2-1$
1363787199	$-9+8^7(7^6(5+4^3)^2)^2+1$	1475726434	$98*((7^6-5)^4)^3)^2+1$
1363787217	$9+8^7(7^6(5+4^3)^2)^2+1$	1475788921	$-9*(8+7)^6+(6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
1364845977	$9*(-8+7^6(5+4^3)^2)^2+1$	1475789191	$9*(8+7)^6+(6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
1364846121	$9*(8+7^6(5+4^3)^2)^2+1$	1475851678	$98*((7^6+5)^4)^3)^2-1$
1367017472	$(9/8*((7^6-5+4)/3)^{-2})^{-1}$	1475851874	$98*((7^6+5)^4)^3)^2+1$
1367929134	$9^8*(7^6/54+32)-1$	1480059378	$(-9+8^7(65)^*(4^3)^2)^2-1$
1372256208	$9*(-8+7^6(5^4)^3)^2+1$	1480070670	$(-9+8^7(65)^*(4^3)^2)^2+1$
1372259664	$9*(8+7^6(5^4)^3)^2+1$	1482418656	$-9+8^7(65^*(4^3)^2)^2-1$
1372670408	$(9/8/(7-(6^5+4)^3)^2)^{-1}$	1482418674	$9+8^7(65^*(4^3)^2)^2-1$
1375900749	$9^8*((7+6-5)^4-3)^{-2-1})$	1482424224	$-9+8^7(65^4)^3)^2-1$
1383542832	$98*(7^6(5-4)^3)^2+1$	1482424242	$9+8^7(65^4)^3)^2-1$
1383561648	$98*(7^6(5+4)^3)^2+1$	1482424398	$-9+8^7(65^4)^3)^2+1$
1407045152	$(98/((7+6)^5+43)^2)^{-1}$	1482424416	$9+8^7(65^4)^3)^2+1$
1409286090	$9+(8^7(7+6-5)^4-3)^2+1$	1482429966	$-9+8^7(65^4)^3)^2+1$
1409286216	$9+(8^7(7+6-5)^4+3)^2+1$	1482429984	$9+8^7(65^4)^3)^2+1$
1410975854	$9^8*(7^6/54+32)-1$	1484777952	$(9+8^7(65)^*(4^3)^2)^2-1$
1410975856	$9^8*(7^6/54+32)+1$	1484789280	$(9+8^7(65)^*(4^3)^2)^2+1$
1417788027	$-9*(8+7^6(5-4^3)^2)^2+1$	1490020812	$-98*(7-65)^*(4^3)^2-1$
1417788171	$9*(8-7^6(5-4^3)^2)^2+1$	1490026398	$-98*((7-65)^4)^3)^2+1$
1418140948	$-98*(7^6(5-4^3)^2)^2+1$	1490026594	$-98*((7-65)^4)^3)^2-1$
1418141144	$-98*(7^6(5-4^3)^2)^2-1$	1490032180	$-98*(7-65)^*(4^3)^2+1$
1418974293	$(9^8-76^5)^*(32+1)$	1491786467	$(9-8^7(6^5)^*(4-321))$
1420466949	$(9^8-7^6)^*(32+1)$	1491789311	$-9-8^7(6^5)^*(4-321)$
1420481733	$(9^8+7^6)^*(32+1)$	1491789329	$9-8^7(6^5)^*(4-321)$
1420491633	$(9^8-76^5)^*(32+1)$	1491792173	$(-9-8^7(6^5)^*(4-321))$
1420518627	$(9^8-(7+6)^5)^*(32+1)$	1500512062	$-98+7*((6+5)^4)^3)^2-1$
1420519221	$(9^8-76^*(5+4))^*(32+1)$	1500512076	$-98+7*((6+5)^4)^3)^2+1$
1420525854	$(9^8-7^*(65+4))^*(32+1)$	1500512088	$-9^8+7*((6+5)^4)^3)^2-1$
1420527702	$(9^8-7^*(65-4))^*(32+1)$	1500512102	$-9^8+7*((6+5)^4)^3)^2+1$
1420527933	$(9^8-7^*(6+54))^*(32+1)$	1500512232	$9^8+7*((6+5)^4)^3)^2-1$
1420530705	$(9^8+7^*(6-54))^*(32+1)$	1500512246	$9^8+7*((6+5)^4)^3)^2+1$
1420531101	$(9^8-(76+5)^4)^*(32+1)$	1500512258	$98+7*((6+5)^4)^3)^2-1$
1420532289	$(9^8-(7+65)^4)^*(32+1)$	1500512272	$98+7*((6+5)^4)^3)^2+1$
1420532421	$(9^8-(76-5)^4)^*(32+1)$	1505040912	$9^8*(7^*(6-5+4)-3)^{-2-1})$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1508229558	$9^8 * (7 * (6 - 5 + 4) + 3^{\wedge}(-2 - 1))$	1575555417	$9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 54 * (32 - 1)$
1510602879	$-9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4) * 321$	1578106691	$(-9 + 8^{\wedge}7 / (6/5)^{\wedge}43) * 21$
1510602897	$9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4) * 321$	1578107069	$(9 + 8^{\wedge}7 / (6/5)^{\wedge}43) * 21$
1510605777	$(9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4)) * 321$	1581966876	$((9^{\wedge}8 * 7 - 6 - 5) / 4 - 3) * 21$
1510620543	$(-9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4)) * 321$	1581966939	$((9^{\wedge}8 * 7 + 6 - 5) / 4 - 3) * 21$
1510623423	$-9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4) * 321$	1581967002	$((9^{\wedge}8 * 7 - 6 - 5) / 4 + 3) * 21$
1510623441	$9 + 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4) * 321$	1581967065	$((9^{\wedge}8 * 7 + 6 - 5) / 4 + 3) * 21$
1529296092	$9 * 87 * ((6 - 5 + 4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	1591084978	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 2 - 1)$
1529296866	$9 * (87 * (6 - 5 + 4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	1591085174	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 2 + 1)$
1529296884	$9 * (87 * (6 - 5 + 4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1592727393	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 * 6 - 5) - 4 * 321$
1529297658	$9 * 87 * ((6 - 5 + 4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1592727774	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 * 6 - 5) - 43 * 21$
1529434075	$(-9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * (4 + 321)$	1592728356	$9^{\wedge}8 * (-7 + (6 + 5)^{\wedge}4) - 321$
1529436991	$-9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4 + 321)$	1592728998	$9^{\wedge}8 * (-7 + (6 + 5)^{\wedge}4) + 321$
1529437009	$9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4 + 321)$	1592729580	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 * 6 - 5) + 43 * 21$
1529439925	$(9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * (4 + 321)$	1592729961	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 * 6 - 5) + 4 * 321$
1531392777	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (32 - 1)$	1601955873	$(-9 + 8 * 765) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
1533201741	$(-9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 543) * (2 + 1)$	1601968095	$(-9 + 8 * 765) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1533201795	$(9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 543) * (2 + 1)$	1602614580	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (-5 + (4 * 3)^{\wedge}2) - 1)$
1533436968	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4 * 32) - 1)$	1602614776	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (-5 + (4 * 3)^{\wedge}2) + 1)$
1533437164	$98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4 * 32) + 1)$	1604315151	$-9 + 8 * 765 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
1534260537	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	1604315169	$9 + 8 * 765 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
1534260681	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21)$	1604321263	$-9 + 8 * (765 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
1536626733	$-9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6) * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21$	1604321297	$9 + 8 * (765 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1536626751	$9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6) * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21$	1604327391	$-9 + 8 * 765 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1536729180	$(-98 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3)) * 21$	1604327409	$9 + 8 * 765 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1536731061	$-9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3)) * 21$	1606674447	$(9 + 8 * 765) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
1536731079	$9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3)) * 21$	1606686705	$(9 + 8 * 765) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1536731140	$-98 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21$	1607811814	$98 * 7 * (6 * 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge} (3/2) - 1)$
1536731336	$98 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21$	1607812402	$98 * (7 * 6 * 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge} (3/2) - 1)$
1536731397	$-9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3)) * 21$	1607812598	$98 * (7 * 6 * 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge} (3/2) + 1)$
1536731415	$9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3)) * 21$	1607813186	$98 * 7 * (6 * 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge} (3/2) + 1)$
1536733296	$(98 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3)) * 21$	1614141193	$(-9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * (4 + 3)^{\wedge} (2 + 1)$
1536835725	$-9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6) * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21$	1614144182	$-98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4 - 32) + 1)$
1536835743	$9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6) * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21$	1614144378	$-98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4 - 32) - 1)$
1540483928	$9 * (-8 + (7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3))^{\wedge}2) - 1$	1614147367	$(9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * (4 + 3)^{\wedge} (2 + 1)$
1540483930	$9 * (-8 + (7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3))^{\wedge}2) + 1$	1616920389	$(9^{\wedge}8 + (7 - 65)^{\wedge}4 * 3) * 21$
1540484072	$9 * (8 + (7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3))^{\wedge}2) - 1$	1629398106	$9^{\wedge}8 * 7 * (6 - (54/32)^{\wedge} - 1)$
1540484074	$9 * (8 + (7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3))^{\wedge}2) + 1$	1630192311	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (32 + 1)$
1542368528	$9 * (8 - 7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3))^{\wedge}2 - 1$	1635772320	$(9 + 87) * 65 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
1542368530	$9 * (8 - 7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1$	1635778464	$(9 + 87) * (65 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
1543558881	$9^{\wedge}8 + 7 * ((6 + 5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge} (3/2) - 1)$	1635778656	$(9 + 87) * (65 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1543558895	$9^{\wedge}8 + 7 * ((6 + 5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge} (3/2) + 1)$	1635784800	$(9 + 87) * 65 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1543790105	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$	1643321232	$9 * 8 / 7^{\wedge} - 6 * (5 * 43 - 21)$
1543790107	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$	1648971837	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (7 * 6 * 5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3) * (-2 - 1)$
1543790249	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$	1660192030	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
1543790251	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$	1660192226	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1550575845	$(98 - 7) * 65 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	1660333150	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
1550581669	$(98 - 7) * (65 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	1660333346	$98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1550581851	$(98 - 7) * (65 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1669850224	$-98 * (7 - 65 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$
1550587675	$(98 - 7) * 65 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	1669851596	$98 * (7 + 65 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$
1551011029	$((-9 - 8) / (7 - (6/5^{\wedge}4 - 4)^{\wedge}3/2))^{\wedge} - 1$	1669856496	$-98 * (7 - 65 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1551449499	$-9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6) * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21$	1669856692	$-98 * (7 - 65 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
1551449517	$9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6) * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21$	1669857378	$98 * ((7 + 6) * 5 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1551552954	$(-98 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3)) * 21$	1669857868	$98 * (7 + 65 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
1551554835	$-9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3)) * 21$	1669858064	$98 * (7 + 65 * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
1551554853	$9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3)) * 21$	1669862964	$-98 * (7 - 65 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1))$
1551554914	$-98 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21$	1669864336	$98 * (7 + 65 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1))$
1551555110	$98 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21$	1677203847	$(-9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (32 + 1)$
1551555171	$-9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3)) * 21$	1677204135	$-9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 54 * (32 + 1)$
1551555189	$9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3)) * 21$	1677204153	$9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 54 * (32 + 1)$
1551557070	$(98 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3)) * 21$	1677204441	$(9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (32 + 1)$
1551660507	$-9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6) * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21$	1678240161	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * (4 - 321)$
1551660525	$9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6) * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21$	1678262913	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4 - 321))$
1558433528	$9 * (8 - 7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3))^{\wedge}2 - 1$	1678263057	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4 - 321))$
1558433530	$9 * (8 - 7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3))^{\wedge}2 + 1$	1678285809	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5) * (4 - 321)$
1560328928	$9 * (-8 + (7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3))^{\wedge}2) - 1$	1679690859	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7 * (65 * 4)^{\wedge}3) * - 21$
1560328930	$9 * (-8 + (7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3))^{\wedge}2) + 1$	1685448000	$((9 + 8) / (765 * 4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge} (-2 + 1)$
1560329072	$9 * (8 + (7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3))^{\wedge}2) - 1$	1688388057	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 * 6 + 5 * (4/3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$
1560329074	$9 * (8 + (7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3))^{\wedge}2) + 1$	1693702467	$9^{\wedge}8 * (-76 / (5/43 - 2) - 1)$
1573037738	$-9 - (87 - 6 * 5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge} (2 + 1)$	1699405137	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4) * 321$
1573037756	$9 - (87 - 6 * 5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge} (2 + 1)$	1699428177	$9 * (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4) * 321)$
1575555129	$(-9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 54) * (32 - 1)$	1699428249	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4) * 321$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1699428321	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*321)$	1789125975	$(98+7)*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1699451289	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*321)$	1789132695	$(98+7)*(65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1699451361	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*321$	1789132905	$(98+7)*(65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1699451433	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*321)$	1789139625	$(98+7)*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1699474473	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*321$	1804854483	$-9^*(8-765*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
1700000000	$(9+8)*(7-6+5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	1804854627	$9^*(8+765*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
1717910600	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$	1804861359	$-9^*(8-765*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1717910796	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$	1804861367	$-9^*(8-765*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
1720060293	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(65^{\wedge}4-3))^*-21$	1804861369	$-9^*(8-765*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
1720061175	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(65^{\wedge}4+3))^*-21$	1804861377	$-9^*(8-765*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1720593225	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+321)$	1804861503	$9^*(8+765*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1720616553	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321))$	1804861511	$9^*(8+765*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
1720616697	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321))$	1804861513	$9^*(8+765*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
1720640025	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321))$	1804861521	$9^*(8+765*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1721865793	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)*5*4-3)^*2-1$	1804868253	$-9^*(8-765*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
1721865795	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)*5*4-3)^*2+1$	1804868397	$9^*(8+765*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
1721865805	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)*5*4+3)^*2-1$	1807943172	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*65)*(43-2+1)$
1721865807	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)*5*4+3)^*2+1$	1807946322	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*65)*(43-2+1)$
1721871873	$((9^{\wedge}8+76)*5*4-3)^*2-1$	1807978242	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*65)*(43-2+1)$
1721871875	$((9^{\wedge}8+76)*5*4-3)^*2+1$	1807981392	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*65)*(43-2+1)$
1721871885	$((9^{\wedge}8+76)*5*4+3)^*2-1$	1811939139	$9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)*4*3-21)$
1721871887	$((9^{\wedge}8+76)*5*4+3)^*2+1$	1811939517	$9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)*4*3+21)$
1724851773	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*543)^*(2+1)$	1821206709	$9^*(8/7^{\wedge}6-5*43+21)$
1724851917	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*543*(2+1))$	1823728851	$9^*(8+765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1724852061	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*543*(2+1))$	1823735799	$9^*((8+765)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1724852205	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*543*(2+1))$	1823735817	$9^*((8+765)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1735950405	$(9^{\wedge}8+76^{\wedge}5/4^{\wedge}3)^*21$	1823742765	$9^*(8+765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1753755300	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3/2))-1)$	1828618335	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54*32-1))$
1756264245	$(-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))^*(2+1)$	1828618479	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54*32-1))$
1756264299	$(9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))^*(2+1)$	1829466305	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*65)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$
1761894576	$(-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2-1))$	1829504980	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*65)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$
1761928272	$(9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2-1))$	1829674935	$9^*((-8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*32-1)$
1763776942	$(-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2+1))$	1829674953	$9^*((-8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*32+1)$
1763810674	$(9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2+1))$	1829677167	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54*32-1)$
1764029106	$98*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)^*(2+1)$	1829677329	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54*32+1)$
1764088875	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}-3^*2)-1)$	1829679543	$9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*32-1)$
1764734901	$(-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4-3))^*(2+1)$	1829679561	$9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*32+1)$
1764734955	$(9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4-3))^*(2+1)$	1830736017	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54*32+1))$
1764735045	$(-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4+3))^*(2+1)$	1830736161	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54*32+1))$
1764735099	$(9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4+3))^*(2+1)$	1835155467	$9^*87*(6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
1764797463	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*6-(5+4)^{\wedge}-3*2-1)$	1835157033	$9^*87*(6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
1764910458	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1)$	1838147878	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}(4*3/2)-1)$
1764914994	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6-((5+4)^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$	1838148074	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}(4*3/2)-1)$
1764916128	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3*2))-1)$	1838383176	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}(4*3/2)+1)$
1764920664	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3-2))-1)$	1838383202	$-9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}(4*3/2)+1)$
1765033659	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3*2-1))$	1838383346	$9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}(4*3/2)+1)$
1765659308	$(-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2-1))$	1838383372	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}(4*3/2)+1)$
1765693076	$(9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2-1))$	1839848742	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*6+5*4/3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
1765742247	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3*2)-1)$	1844723678	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*32-1$
1767541674	$(-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1))$	1844723874	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*32+1$
1767575478	$(9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1))$	1844736418	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4^{\wedge}3/2+1)$
1772497602	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1))$	1844748766	$98*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*32-1)$
1772499762	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1))$	1844748962	$98*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*32+1)$
1772499906	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1))$	1849681008	$98*(7+65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1772502066	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1))$	1849687966	$98*(7+65)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
1773205701	$(-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^*(2+1)$	1849688162	$98*(7+65)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
1773205755	$(9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))^*(2+1)$	1849695120	$98*(7+65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1776075822	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*6-5*4/3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	1850182317	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}-3*2)+1)$
1778661766	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*(65^{\wedge}4/3))^*21$	1850300496	$9^{\wedge}8/(7+(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
1779795909	$9^{\wedge}8*(-76/(5/43-2)+1)$	1850890905	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*6-(5+4)^{\wedge}-3*2+1)$
1784500023	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$	1851003900	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1)$
1784500041	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$	1851008436	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6-((5+4)^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$
1785980259	$-9^*(8-765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	1851008682	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*6+5-4)-321$
1785987063	$-9^*(8-765)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	1851009324	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*6+5-4)+321$
1785987081	$-9^*((8-765)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	1851009570	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3*2))+1)$
1785993885	$-9^*(8-765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	1851014106	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1)$
1787076158	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*(32-1)$	1851127101	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3*2+1)$
1787100462	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*(32-1)$	1851835689	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3*2)+1)$
1787776045	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7/6)*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	1855402329	$9^{\wedge}8*-76+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3*21$
1787812873	$(-9+8^{\wedge}7/(6/5))*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	1862030723	$98*7^{\wedge}6*(54*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
1787831287	$(9+8^{\wedge}7/(6/5))*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	1862169264	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3/2))+1)$
1787868115	$(9+8^{\wedge}7/6)*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	1867794642	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3)^*(2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
1867795475	$98^{*(7^6*54^3*2^{\wedge}-1)}$	1980170096	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*65)^*(43+2+1)$
1867795573	$98^{*(7^6*54^3*2^{\wedge}-1)}$	1983209120	$9^{*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2))}-1$
1867796406	$98^{*(7^6*54+3)^*(2+1)}$	1983209122	$9^{*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2))+1}$
1872512571	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*65)^*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	1983209264	$9^{*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2))-1}$
1872552156	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*65)^*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	1983209266	$9^{*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2))+1}$
1873560325	$98^{*7^{\wedge}6*(54^3*2^{\wedge}-1)}$	1985191686	$9^{*((-8+7^{\wedge}6)*5^{\wedge}4*3-21)}$
1881194697	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}(4^3/2))-1$	1985192064	$9^{*((-8+7^{\wedge}6)*5^{\wedge}4*3+21)}$
1881429995	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}(4^3/2)+1)$	1985461686	$9^{*((8+7^{\wedge}6)*5^{\wedge}4*3-21)}$
1882266253	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1985462064	$9^{*((8+7^{\wedge}6)*5^{\wedge}4*3+21)}$
1882266423	$9^{*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3*2-1)}$	1986121495	$-98+(7+6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
1882266449	$98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1986121521	$-9^{*8+(7+6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)}$
1882501551	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	1986121665	$9^{*8+(7+6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)}$
1882501721	$9^{*8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3*2+1)}$	1986121691	$98+(7+6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
1882501747	$98+7^{\wedge}6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	1986526458	$9^{\wedge}8*7^{*(6+(54/32)^{\wedge}-1)}$
1886852286	$9^{*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(32+1)}$	1987444484	$9^{*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2))-1}$
1886854590	$9^{*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*54^*(32+1))}$	1987444486	$9^{*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2))+1}$
1886854734	$9^{*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54^*(32+1))}$	1987444628	$9^{*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2))-1}$
1886857038	$9^{*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(32+1)}$	1987444630	$9^{*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2))+1}$
1890854630	$98^{*(7^{\wedge}6*(54^3*2-1)-1)}$	1988120781	$9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3*2-1)$
1890854826	$98^{*(7^{\wedge}6*(54^3*2+1)+1)}$	1997686719	$9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3*2+1)$
1894035704	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*65)^*(43+2-1)$	2007562464	$9^{*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21))}$
1894039004	$(9^{\wedge}8-76*5)^*(43+2-1)$	2007562608	$9^{*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21))}$
1894072444	$(9^{\wedge}8+76*5)^*(43+2-1)$	2015617518	$-9-(87-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1894075744	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*65)^*(43+2-1)$	2015617536	$9-(87-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1894469067	$9^{\wedge}8/(7^{*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)+2})^{\wedge}-1$	2015632896	$-9-(87-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1896619482	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	2015632914	$9-(87-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1896619576	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	2020538682	$9^{\wedge}8^{*((7-6/(5+4)/3)^{\wedge}2+1)}$
1902371394	$98^{*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^*(32+1)}$	2022480783	$9^{*(8^{*(7/6-5^{\wedge}4*3)})^{\wedge}2-1}$
1902397266	$98^{*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)^*(32+1)}$	2022480785	$9^{*(8^{*(7/6-5^{\wedge}4*3)})^{\wedge}2+1}$
1920495809	$-98-(7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	2022840575	$9^{*(8^{*(7-6-5^{\wedge}4*3)})^{\wedge}2-1}$
1920495835	$-9^{*8}-(7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	2022840577	$9^{*(8^{*(7-6-5^{\wedge}4*3)})^{\wedge}2+1}$
1920495979	$9^{*8}-(7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	2023194603	$9^{\wedge}8^{*(7^*6+5)-4^*321}$
1920496005	$98-(7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	2023194984	$9^{\wedge}8^{*(7^*6+5)-43^*21}$
1925313072	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	2023195566	$9^{\wedge}8^{*(-7+6^*(5+4))-321}$
1925548370	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	2023195605	$(9-8^*7)^*(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
1926972899	$9^{*-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))}$	2023196169	$(9-8^*7)^*(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
1926973043	$9^{*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))}$	2023196208	$9^{\wedge}8^{*(-7+6^*(5+4))+321}$
1926973069	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$	2023196790	$9^{\wedge}8^{*(7^*6+5)+43^*21}$
1928149389	$-9^{*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))}$	2023197171	$9^{\wedge}8^{*(7^*6+5)+4^*321}$
1928149533	$9^{*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))}$	2027160575	$9^{*(8^{*(7-6+5^{\wedge}4*3)})^{\wedge}2-1}$
1928149559	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$	2027160577	$9^{*(8^{*(7-6+5^{\wedge}4*3)})^{\wedge}2+1}$
1929229137	$9^{*(-87+(6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1}$	2028264881	$(-9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(432-1)$
1929229155	$9^{*(-87+(6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)}$	2028268769	$9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*5^*(432-1)$
1929230721	$9^{*(87+(6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)}$	2028570075	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7-65^{\wedge}4)^*3)^*21$
1934250632	$9^{*-8^{\wedge}7+(6^*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)}$	2028570957	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7+65^{\wedge}4)^*3)^*21$
1937103129	$(9^{\wedge}8+76/5)/(43+2)^{\wedge}-1$	2029168314	$9^{\wedge}8+(7+6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
1953124865	$-9^{*(8+7)+(6^*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)}$	2032974703	$-9+8^{*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*432-1)}$
1953125135	$9^{*(8+7)+(6^*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)}$	2032974737	$9+8^{*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*432+1)}$
1963542628	$9^{\wedge}8-(7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	2036588869	$-98-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1964205936	$98^{*7/(6/(5+4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)}$	2036588895	$-9^{*8}-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1965783696	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*65^{\wedge}4)^*(-3-21)$	2036589039	$9^{*8}-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1966077111	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4-321)}$	2036589065	$98-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1966079433	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4-3^*21)}$	2036604407	$-98-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1966079703	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4-32-1)}$	2036604433	$-9^{*8}-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1966079721	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4-32+1)}$	2036604577	$9^{*8}-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1966079784	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4-3-21)}$	2036604603	$98-(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1966079838	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4-3-21)}$	2037676783	$(-9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(432+1)$
1966080162	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4-3+21)}$	2037680671	$-9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*5^*(432+1)$
1966080216	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5^{\wedge}4)+3+21)}$	2037680689	$9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*5^*(432+1)$
1966080279	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4+32-1)}$	2037684577	$(9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(432+1)$
1966080297	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5^{\wedge}4)+32+1)}$	2038033610	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))+1)$
1966080567	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5^{\wedge}4)+3^*21)}$	2038033644	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2))-1)$
1966082889	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5^{\wedge}4)+321)}$	2038423833	$-9^{*(8+7)+6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)}$
1971561942	$98^{*7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)^*(2+1)}$	2038423967	$(-9+8)^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1971999368	$9^{*8^{\wedge}7+(6^*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)}$	2038424103	$9^{*(8+7)+6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)}$
1975516995	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/(5^{\wedge}4+3)))-21}$	2038439385	$-9^{*(8+7)+6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)}$
1975517373	$9^{*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/(5^{\wedge}4+3)))+21}$	2038439519	$(-9+8)^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
1978137938	$98^{*7^{*(6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1}}$	2038439655	$9^{*(8+7)+6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)}$
1978138722	$98^{*(7^{*(6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1})}$	2038453095	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1980128236	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*65)^*(43+2+1)$	2038541455	$(-9-8)^{\wedge}7+(6^{\wedge}5/4)^{\wedge}3/(2+1)$
1980131686	$(9^{\wedge}8-76*5)^*(43+2+1)$	2040258871	$-98+(7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
1980166646	$(9^{\wedge}8+76*5)^*(43+2+1)$	2040258897	$-9^{*8}+(7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
2040259041	$9 \cdot 8 + (7+6^5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$		
2040259067	$98 + (7+6^5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$		
2040274437	$-98 + (7+6^5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2040274463	$-9 \cdot 8 + (7+6^5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2040274607	$9 \cdot 8 + (7+6^5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2040274633	$98 + (7+6^5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2042517362	$(9 / (8 + 7 \cdot 6^5 \cdot 5^{(4+3) \cdot 2}))^{-1}$		
2047946735	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^6-5) \cdot 4^{(3+2)-1})$		
2047946769	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^6-5) \cdot 4^{(3+2)+1})$		
2048033775	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^6(6/5) \cdot 4)^{(3+2)-1})$		
2048033809	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^6(6/5) \cdot 4)^{(3+2)+1})$		
2048120815	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^6+5) \cdot 4^{(3+2)-1})$		
2048120849	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^6+5) \cdot 4^{(3+2)+1})$		
2053177343	$9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7+6+5 \cdot 4^3))^2 - 1$		
2053177345	$9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7+6+5 \cdot 4^3))^2 + 1$		
2054938977	$9 \cdot (876-5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$		
2054946807	$9 \cdot ((876-5) \cdot 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$		
2054946825	$9 \cdot ((876-5) \cdot 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2054954655	$9 \cdot (876-5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2057298336	$9/8^{\wedge} - 7+6^5 \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$		
2057313888	$9/8^{\wedge} - 7+6^5 \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2058033940	$(9+8) \cdot (7^6 \cdot (5+4^{(3+2)})) - 1$		
2058033974	$(9+8) \cdot (7^6 \cdot (5+4^{(3+2)})) + 1$		
2061230400	$-9 + (87+6^5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$		
2061230418	$9 + (87+6^5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$		
2061246126	$-9 + (87+6^5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2061246144	$9 + (87+6^5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2065424697	$(9 \cdot 876 - 5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$		
2065440455	$(9 \cdot 876 - 5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2066695992	$-9 \cdot 876 \cdot (5 - 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2066703867	$-9 \cdot (876 \cdot (5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) + 1)$		
2066703885	$-9 \cdot (876 \cdot (5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) - 1)$		
2066711760	$-9 \cdot 876 \cdot (5 - 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$		
2066774832	$9 \cdot 876 \cdot (5 + 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$		
2066782707	$9 \cdot (876 \cdot (5 + 4^3 \cdot 2) - 1)$		
2066782725	$9 \cdot (876 \cdot (5 + 4^3 \cdot 2) + 1)$		
2066790600	$9 \cdot 876 \cdot (5 + 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2068046127	$(9 \cdot 876 + 5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$		
2068061905	$(9 \cdot 876 + 5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2074195279	$(-9-8) \cdot ((7^6-5^{\wedge}(4 \cdot 3)) / 2 + 1)$		
2074195313	$(-9-8) \cdot ((7^6-5^{\wedge}(4 \cdot 3)) / 2 - 1)$		
2076195312	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^6+5^{\wedge}(4 \cdot 3)) / 2 - 1)$		
2076195346	$(9+8) \cdot ((7^6+5^{\wedge}(4 \cdot 3)) / 2 + 1)$		
2078531847	$9 \cdot (876+5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$		
2078539767	$9 \cdot ((876+5) \cdot 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$		
2078539785	$9 \cdot ((876+5) \cdot 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2078547705	$9 \cdot (876+5) \cdot (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2080374793	$9+8^{\wedge}(7+6-5) \cdot 4 \cdot (32-1)$		
2107695006	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot (7 \cdot (6+5-4) - 3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$		
2116736063	$9 / (8 \cdot (7 \cdot 6 + 5 \cdot 4^3))^{\wedge} - 2 - 1$		
2116736065	$9 / (8 \cdot (7 \cdot 6 + 5 \cdot 4^3))^{\wedge} - 2 + 1$		
2118855267	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot (7 \cdot 6 + 5 \cdot (4/3 \cdot 2 + 1))$		
2133449595	$(9+8) \cdot ((7+6)^{\wedge}(-5+4 \cdot 3) \cdot 2 + 1)$		
2133843741	$-9 + (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 \cdot (5^{\wedge} 4 / 3 - 21)$		
2133843759	$9 + (8+7)^{\wedge} 6 \cdot (5^{\wedge} 4 / 3 - 21)$		
2137499928	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot (76 \cdot 5^{\wedge} 4^{\wedge}(3/2) - 1)$		
2137500072	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot (76 \cdot 5^{\wedge} 4^{\wedge}(3/2) + 1)$		

Supplement 3

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-30085	$-1-2-(3^4*5-67)*89$	-85386	$-12+3^4*(5-67)*(8+9)$
-30354	$12-3^4*5*(67+8)+9$	-85431	$(1+(2^3-4^5/(6/7)))^8)^9$
-31676	$1-(2+3^4*56)^7+89$	-85611	$(1+(2+(3-4^5)/(6/7)))^8)^9$
-36218	$(1+2)*(3^4-(5^6*7+8)/9)$	-85647	$(1+(2+3-4^5/(6/7)))^8)^9$
-38334	$-12-3^4*(5+6*78)-9$	-85665	$(-1+(2+3-4^5/(6/7)))^8)^9$
-40039	$1^*2-(3^4+56*78)^9$	-85917	$(1+(2-(3-4^5)/(6/7)))^8)^9$
-40043	$1^*-2-(3^4+56*78)^9$	-86367	$(1-(2+3+4^5/(6/7)))^8)^9$
-40124	$1^*-2-(3^4*56-78)^9$	-86421	$(1+(2+(3+4^5)/(6/7)))^8)^9$
-40197	$-12+3^4*(5-67)*8-9$	-86439	$(1-(2^*3+4^5/(6/7)))^8)^9$
-40947	$12-(3^4*56+7+8)^9$	-86601	$(1+(2^3+4^5/(6/7)))^8)^9$
-41195	$12-((3^4-5)^6+7)^89$	-87597	$(1-(2/3^4-5)^*(6+7)*8)^9$
-42005	$1+2-(3^4*5+67)^89$	-87944	$-12-(3^4-5)^*(6+7)*89$
-42270	$12+3^4*(5-67*8+9)$	-91417	$(1-2/3^4-4^5)*((6+7)^8+9)$
-43842	$-12-3^4*(5+67*8)-9$	-91842	$12+3^4*(5-67*(8+9))$
-45213	$-1+2*(3^4-5*67)^89$	-93131	$1-2*(3^4*(567+8)-9)$
-47302	$1^*2-3^4*(567+8+9)$	-93133	$-1-2*(3^4*(567+8)-9)$
-49548	$-12-(3^4+5)^6*(7+89)$	-93169	$-1-2*(3^4*(567+8)+9)$
-50259	$(-1-2)*((3+4)^5+6*(7-8)^9)$	-94134	$-12-3^4*(5+67)*89$
-51288	$12-(3^4-5)^*(67+8)^9$	-94923	$(1+2*(3^4*5*(6+7)+8))^9$
-51918	$12-((3^4+5)^6+7+8)^9$	-95486	$1/(2+3+4)-5^6*(7-8)/9$
-53043	$12-3^4*5*(6*7+89)$	-98158	$(12+(3^4+5)^6*7)*(-8-9)$
-53050	$12+(3^4+5)^*(6-7*89)$	-99132	$12-3^4*(5+67)*(8+9)$
-54106	$-12-(3^4+5)^*(6+7*89)$	-99514	$-12-(3^4+5)^*(6+7)*89$
-54412	$12*(3^4*56+(7+8)/9)$	-100698	$(1-(2^*3)^4/5)^6*(7^*8+9)$
-54452	$-12*(3^4*56+(7+8)/9)$	-101125	$(1-2/3^4-4^5)^*(6+7*(8+9))$
-54476	$1/(2/((3^4-5^6)*7))-8^9$	-104361	$(1-2/3^4-4^5)*(-6+(7+8)^9)$
-55068	$12-3^4*(5+(67+8)^9)$	-105494	$-1/2-(3/4*(5^6-7)+8)^9$
-55716	$12+(3^4+5)^*(6-78)^9$	-105808	$(-1+(2-3^4*(5+6))^7)^*(8+9)$
-58038	$12-(3^4+5)^*(67+8)^9$	-105958	$(-1+2^3-3/4)^*(5^6*7-8+9)$
-58062	$-12-(3^4+5)^*(67+8)^9$	-106218	$(-1-2)*(3^4*5+6^7/8+9)$
-58251	$-12-3^4*(5+6*7*(8+9))$	-107940	$(1-((2^*3)^4-5)/6)^7*8^9$
-60159	$12*(3^4*(5-67)+8)+9$	-108511	$(1-2*(3^4-5)^6*7)^*(8+9)$
-60163	$1-2*(3^4*5-67)*89$	-109007	$1+2*(3^4*(5-678)+9)$
-60177	$12*(3^4*(5-67)+8)-9$	-109009	$-1+2*(3^4*(5-678)+9)$
-60843	$-12+3^4*(5-(6+78)^9)$	-111065	$(-1-2^3*(4+(5^6-7)^8))/9$
-61295	$(1+(2/3^4-4-5)^6)^*(7-8^9)$	-112113	$(1-2*(3^4*(5+6)^7-8))^9$
-61653	$-12-3^4*(5+(6+78)^9)$	-112794	$(-1-2^3-3/4)^*(5^6*7-8+9)$
-62044	$12^*3*(4-(5^6-78)/9)$	-113599	$(1+(2-3^4*5)^6)^*(7^*8-9)$
-62867	$1+(2-3^4*5)^*(67+89)$	-113693	$(-1+(2-3^4*5)^6)^*(7^*8-9)$
-62956	$-12^*3*(4+(5^6+78)/9)$	-114727	$(1-(2+3^4*5)^6)^*(7^*8-9)$
-63826	$1^*2-3^4*(5-6+789)$	-114821	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^6)^*(7^*-8+9)$
-63841	$1/2+3^4*(5/6-789)$	-115195	$-1-(2*(3^4*5-6)^*789)$
-63842	$-1/2+3^4*(5/6-789)$	-115765	$(1-2/3^4-4*(5+6))^*(7^*8+9)$
-63977	$-1/2-3^4*(5/6+789)$	-115884	$-12*(3^4+5^6)^*(78+9)$
-64802	$1^*-2-3^4*(5+6+789)$	-116645	$(1+2/3)/(4/(5-6^7-8-9))$
-66027	$-12-3^4*(5+6*(7+8)^9)$	-121519	$(1+(2^*3+4)^*(5^6*7-8))/9$
-67375	$-1-((2^3)^4+5^6*78)^9$	-125379	$(1-2^*3^4*(5^6+7^*8))^9$
-69231	$-12^*((3^4+5)^6+7+8)+9$	-125397	$(1+2^*3^4*(5^6+7^*8))^9$
-69477	$12-3^4*(5+6)^*78+9$	-126562	$1/2+3^4*5^6/(7-8-9)$
-70188	$-12*(3^4*(5+67)+8+9)$	-126563	$-1/2+3^4*5^6/(7-8-9)$
-71901	$(-1-2)*(3^4*(5^6+7)^8-9)$	-127287	$(1-2*(3^4*(5+6)-7)^8)^9$
-72590	$-1^*2-(3^4+5+6)^*789$	-129455	$(-1-2/3^4-4*(5+6*7))^*(8+9)$
-73050	$12+3^4*(5+6)^*(7-89)$	-133983	$(1+(2-3^4*(5^6-7))^8)^9$
-74497	$(1+(2/3^4-4-5)^6)^*(-7-8^9)$	-134001	$(-1+(2-3^4*(5^6-7))^8)^9$
-75912	$-12*(3^4*(5+6)^*7+89)$	-135430	$-12-(3^4+5^6*78)/9$
-76855	$(1-2/3^4-4^5)*((6+7)^8-9)$	-138513	$1-23^4+(5^6+78)^9$
-76981	$12-(3^4*56-7)^*(8+9)$	-139182	$12+(3^4-5^6+78)^9$
-77045	$(-1-2/3^4-4^5)*((6+7)^8-9)$	-139854	$1+2^*34-(5^6-78)^9$
-77505	$12-3^4*(5+6)^*(78+9)$	-140255	$1+234-(5^6-7-8)^9$
-78664	$12-(3^4*(5+6)-7)^*89$	-140257	$-1+234-(5^6-7-8)^9$
-78688	$-12-(3^4*(5+6)-7)^*89$	-140857	$(-1-2/3^4-4*(5+6))^*(7+8^9)$
-78884	$12*(3^4-5/6)^*(7-89)$	-140894	$1+234-(5^6+7^*8)^9$
-80083	$-1-2*(3^4+56*78)^9$	-140993	$1-234-(5^6+7+8)^9$
-80838	$12^*3^4*(5/6*7-89)$	-140995	$-1-234-(5^6+7+8)^9$
-82086	$12-3/4*(5^6*7+89)$	-141396	$12-3^4-(5^6+78)^9$
-83051	$1-2*(3^4*56+78)^9$	-142068	$-12-(3^4+5^6+78)^9$
-83053	$-1-2*(3^4*56+78)^9$	-149715	$(-1-2)*(3^4*(5+6)^7*8+9)$
-83596	$12*(3-4*(5^6+7^*8)/9)$	-157235	$(-1+(2-3^4*5)^6)^*(7^*8+9)$
-83694	$-12*(3^4-5/6)^*(78+9)$	-158665	$(1-(2+3^4*5)^6)^*(7^*8+9)$
-83707	$(1-2/3^4-4*(5+6))^*(7^*8-9)$	-164739	$(12-3^4*(5^6-7))^*89$
-83801	$(-1-2^*3^4*(5+6))^*(7^*8-9)$	-169512	$(-1+2*(3-4^5/6))^7*8^9$
-85348	$1+2-(3^4+56)^*7^*89$	-171987	$(-1+2*(3-4^5/(6/7/8)))^9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-172077	$(1-2*(3+4^5/(6/7/8)))^*9$	-247851	$(1-2*3^4*5*(6*7-8))^*9$
-172095	$(-1-2*(3+4^5/(6/7/8)))^*9$	-247869	$(-1-2/3^4-4*5*(6*7-8))^*9$
-174303	$(1+(2-3^4*5*6+7)*8)^*9$	-250938	$(1+2)^*3^4*(-5^6/(7+8)+9)$
-174321	$(-1+(2-3^4*5*6+7)*8)^*9$	-257376	$(1+(2-3/4^5)/6)^*7*8*9$
-174552	$(1-2*(3+4^5/6))^*7*8*9$	-260199	$(1-(2+(3^4+5)*6*7)*8)^*9$
-175599	$(1-(2+3^4*5*6+7)*8)^*9$	-260217	$(1+(2+(3^4+5)*6*7)*8)^*-9$
-176402	$-1/2-((3+4)^5/(6/7)-8)^*9$	-261063	$(1-(2+(3^4+5)*6)^*7*8)^*9$
-176546	$-1/2-((3+4)^5/(6/7)+8)^*9$	-261081	$(1+(2+(3^4+5)*6)^*7*8)^*-9$
-178167	$(1-(2^3)^4*(5-6^7(7-8)))^*9$	-261689	$(1+(2^3)^4*(567+8))/-9$
-178185	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5-6^7(7-8)))^*-9$	-262293	$(12+3^4*5)^*(-6-7*89)$
-178993	$(1-2/3^4-4*5*(6+7))^*(8+9)$	-262452	$-12+3^4*5*(6-78)^*9$
-179027	$(1+2/3^4-4*5*(6+7))^*(-8-9)$	-264543	$(1-2*3^4*5)^*(6*7*8-9)$
-192839	$(1-(2+3^4*5)*6)^*(7+8*9)$	-265197	$(-1-2/3^4-4*5)^*(6*7*8-9)$
-192997	$(1+(2+3^4*5)*6)^*(-7-8*9)$	-270330	$(1-(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(7+8-9)$
-194423	$(1+2*(3^4-5^6*7)*8)/9$	-270342	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(-7-8+9)$
-194443	$(1+2*(3/4-5^6*7)*8)/9$	-273195	$(1-(2^3)^4)^*(5+6/7*8*9)$
-198659	$12/(3+4)-5^6/7*89$	-273267	$(12-3^4*5*(67+8))^*9$
-200943	$(1+(2-(3^4*5-6)^*7)*8)^*9$	-273427	$(-1-2/3/4)^*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$
-200961	$(-1+(2-(3^4*5-6)^*7)*8)^*9$	-273448	$(-1-2/3/4)^*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$
-201231	$(1-(2+(3^4*5-6)^*7)*8)^*9$	-274239	$(1-(2+3^4*(5+6*7))^*8)^*9$
-206292	$-12*(3^4-4*5*6^7-89)$	-274257	$(1+(2+3^4*(5+6*7))^*8)^*-9$
-207111	$(12-3^4*5)^*(67*8-9)$	-281109	$(-1-2)^*((3/4*5^6-7)*8+9)$
-207279	$(1-(2+(3^4*5+6)^*7)*8)^*9$	-281391	$(-1-2)^*((3/4*5^6+7)*8-9)$
-208428	$-12*(3^4-4*5*6^7+89)$	-281445	$(-1-2)^*((3/4*5^6+7)*8+9)$
-212075	$(-1-2/3^4-4*(5+6)^*7)^*(8+9)$	-282491	$1+2*(3^4-(5^6+78)^*9)$
-213180	$12-3^4*5^6*(7*8-9)$	-282493	$-1+2*(3^4-(5^6+78)^*9)$
-213204	$-12-3^4*5^6*(7*8-9)$	-282586	$1*2*(34-(5^6+78)^*9)$
-213423	$12-3^4*5^6*(67*8-9)$	-282667	$1-2*(3+4+(5^6+78)^*9)$
-213447	$-12-3^4*5^6*(67*8-9)$	-282723	$-1-2*(34+(5^6+78)^*9)$
-214185	$(12-3^4*5)^*(67*8+9)$	-286706	$(1-(2^3)^4*5)^*(6+7-8+9)$
-214947	$(12-3^4*5)^*(67-8)^*9$	-286734	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(-6-7+8-9)$
-215043	$12-3^4*5^6*(67-8)^*9$	-287725	$(1+(2-3^4*5)^*6*7)^*(8+9)$
-215067	$-12-3^4*5^6*(67-8)^*9$	-288414	$(12-(3^4*5+6)^*78)^*9$
-215163	$(12+3^4*5^6*(67-8))^*-9$	-288915	$(1+(2-3^4*5^6)^*7)^*(8+9)$
-215919	$(1-(2+3^4*(5*6+7))^*8)^*9$	-288949	$(-1+(2-3^4*5^6)^*7)^*(8+9)$
-217437	$1+2*((3^4-5^6)^*7+89)$	-289391	$(1-(2+3^4*5^6)^*7)^*(8+9)$
-217793	$1+2*((3^4-5^6)^*7-89)$	-289425	$(1+(2+3^4*5^6)^*7)^*(-8-9)$
-217795	$-1+2*((3^4-5^6)^*7-89)$	-290581	$(1-(2+3^4*5^6)^*6*7)^*(8+9)$
-218641	$-1-2*(34+5^6*7-89)$	-290615	$(1+(2+3^4*5^6)^*6*7)^*(-8-9)$
-218859	$1+2*(34-5^6*7-89)$	-291708	$(12+3^4*(5^6*7+8))^*9$
-218995	$1-2*(34+5^6*7+89)$	-294507	$(1-2*3^4*(5^6*7-8))^*9$
-218996	$-1*2*(34+5^6*7+89)$	-294525	$(1+2*3^4*(5^6*7-8))^*-9$
-219089	$1-2*(3^4+5^6*7+89)$	-306027	$(1-2*(3^4*5^6*7-8))^*9$
-219091	$-1-2*(3^4+5^6*7+89)$	-306333	$(1+2*(3^4*5^6*7+8))^*-9$
-219705	$1-2*((3^4+5^6)^*7-89)$	-307185	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6/(7-8)-9)$
-219707	$-1-2*((3^4+5^6)^*7-89)$	-307215	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6/(7-8)-9)$
-220061	$1-2*((3^4+5^6)^*7+89)$	-310023	$(1-((2^3)^4+5^6*7)^*8)^*9$
-220063	$-1-2*((3^4+5^6)^*7+89)$	-310041	$(1+((2^3)^4+5^6*7)^*8)^*-9$
-220713	$12-3^4*5^6*(67*8+9)$	-310841	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+678))/-9$
-224883	$(-1+(2-3^4*5)^*(6+7*8))^*9$	-313145	$(1-2*3^4)^*((5^6+7)/8-9)$
-224900	$-1/(2+3)^*(4+(5^6-7)^*8*9)$	-314765	$1-(23^4-56+7)/8*9$
-227097	$(1-(2+3^4*5)^*(6+7*8))^*9$	-315835	$(1-2/(3^4-4/5)^*6)^*(7*8+9)$
-227115	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^*(6+7*8))^*-9$	-315965	$(-1-2/3^4-4*5^6)^*(7*8+9)$
-228373	$(1-2/(3^4-4/5)^*6)^*(7*8-9)$	-316043	$(1-2*3^4)^*((5^6+7)/8+9)$
-228467	$(-1-2/3^4-4*5^6)^*(7*8-9)$	-317035	$(-1-2*3^4)^*((5^6+7)/8-9)$
-229671	$(1+(2-(3^4-5)^*6*7)*8)^*9$	-317736	$-12*(3^4*(5^6*7-8)-9)$
-229977	$(1+(2+(3^4-5)^*6*7)*8)^*-9$	-319098	$(1-(2^3)^4/5)^*6*(7*8+9)$
-230823	$(1-(2+(3^4-5)^*6)^*7*8)^*9$	-319423	$(1-(2^3)^4/(5/6))^*(7*8+9)$
-232245	$(-1+2^2(3^4))^*(5-6/(7/8/9))$	-319553	$(1+(2^3)^4/(5/6))^*(7-8*9)$
-236366	$-12*((3+4)^5/(6/7)+89)$	-319969	$(-1-2*3^4)^*((5^6+7)/8+9)$
-238491	$(12+3^4*(5^6*7-8))^*-9$	-320220	$(12+(3^4-5)^*6*78)^*-9$
-240561	$(1-2/3^4-4*(5+6)^*(7+8))^*9$	-321456	$12-(3^4+5)^*6*7*89$
-240579	$(-1-2/3^4-4*(5+6)^*(7+8))^*9$	-324756	$-12*3^4*(5^6*7-8/9)$
-242481	$(-12+3^4*5)^*(6-7*89)$	-325980	$(12-(3^4*5^6-7)^*8)^*9$
-243051	$(1-(2+3)^*(4*5^6*7-8))/9$	-326196	$(12+(3^4*5^6-7)^*8)^*-9$
-244233	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+(6+7)/8))^*-9$	-326373	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5^6)^*7+8+9)$
-245750	$(-1+2^2(3+4+5)^*6)^*(7-8-9)$	-326421	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5^6)^*7-8+9)$
-245770	$(1+2^2(3+4+5)^*6)^*(7-8-9)$	-326427	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5^6)^*7+8-9)$
-246105	$(-1+2*(3-4-5^6*7)/8)^*9$	-326475	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5^6)^*7-8-9)$
-246267	$(1-2*(3^4+5^6*7)/8)^*9$	-327204	$(12+(3^4*5^6+7)^*8)^*-9$
-246285	$(-1-2*(3^4+5^6*7)/8)^*9$	-327666	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6*7+8*9)$
-247197	$(12-3^4*5)^*(6+7*89)$	-327756	$(1+2)^*(34-5^6*7+89)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-327789	$(-1+(2-3^4*5^6)*(7+8))^9$	-402882	$(-1+2*3^4*5)^*(6-7*8^9)$
-327831	$(1+2)*(3^4-5^6*7+8+9)$	-403878	$(1+2/(3^4-4/5))*(6-7*8^9)$
-328407	$-1-2-3*(4+5^6*7+8+9)$	-404387	$-1+23*(4-(5^6+7)/8^9)$
-328419	$(-1-2)*(3^4+5^6*7+8+9)$	-405859	$1-234*(5^6-7-8)/9$
-328494	$(-1-2)*(3^4+5^6*7+8+9)$	-405861	$-1-234*(5^6-7-8)/9$
-328584	$(-1-2)*(3^4+5^6*7+8+9)$	-406225	$-1-234*(5^6+7-8)/9$
-329610	$(-1-2)*((3^4+5^6)*7-8^9)$	-406235	$1+2+3*(4-5^6*78/9)$
-329661	$(1-(2+3^4*5)^6*(7+8))^9$	-406236	$1*2+3*(4-5^6*78/9)$
-329679	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^6*(7+8))^9$	-406237	$-1+2+3*(4-5^6*78/9)$
-329775	$(-1-2)*((3^4+5^6)*7-8-9)$	-406275	$1-234*(5^6-7+8)/9$
-329829	$(-1-2)*((3^4+5^6)*7-8+9)$	-406639	$1-234*(5^6+7+8)/9$
-329877	$(-1-2)*((3^4+5^6)*7+8+9)$	-407492	$1+(2-3^4*(567-8))^9$
-330042	$(-1-2)*((3^4+5^6)*7+8^9)$	-407494	$-1+(2-3^4*(567-8))^9$
-333321	$(-1-2*(3^4/5^6-7)*8)/9$	-407528	$1-(2+3^4*(567-8))^9$
-337635	$(-12+3^4*(5-6*78))^9$	-407530	$-1-(2+3^4*(567-8))^9$
-342552	$(1+2/3*(4^5-6))^7*8^9$	-408701	$1-(2+(3^4+5)^6)*789$
-344709	$(12-3^4*(5+6*78))^9$	-408703	$-1-(2+(3^4+5)^6)*789$
-344925	$(12+3^4*(5+6*78))^9$	-412590	$(1-2/(3^4-4/5))^*(6+7*8^9)$
-348903	$(1-2*(3^4*5^6-7)*8)^9$	-413252	$1+(2-3^4*567+8)^9$
-348921	$(1+2*(3^4*5^6-7)*8)^9$	-413288	$1-(2+3^4*567-8)^9$
-350919	$(1-2*(3^4*5^6+7)*8)^9$	-413290	$-1-(2+3^4*567-8)^9$
-350937	$(1+2*(3^4*5^6+7)*8)^9$	-413396	$1+(2-3^4*567-8)^9$
-351373	$(12^4(3-4+5)-67)^*(-8-9)$	-413398	$-1+(2-3^4*567-8)^9$
-352794	$(1-2*((3+4)^5/(6/7)-8))^9$	-413434	$-1-(2+3^4*567+8)^9$
-353100	$(-1-2*((3+4)^5/(6/7)+8))^9$	-413610	$(1+2*3^4*5)^*(-6-7*8^9)$
-353651	$(12^4(3-4+5)+67)^*(-8-9)$	-414693	$(-1-2)*(3^4-4*5^6*7^8-9)$
-355752	$-12*3^4*(5*(67+8)-9)$	-414747	$(-1-2)*(3^4-4*5^6*7^8+9)$
-358137	$-1-((2^3)^4-5-67)*89$	-414756	$(12-(3^4+5)*67*8)^9$
-358938	$-1-((2^3)^4-56-7)*89$	-414852	$12-(3^4+5)*67*8^9$
-360184	$-1-((2^3)^4-56+7)*89$	-414972	$(12+(3^4+5)*67*8)^9$
-360440	$(1-(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(7-8+9)$	-418608	$-12*(3^4-5)^*(6*78-9)$
-361361	$1-(2+(3^4-5)^6)*789$	-419156	$1+(2-3^4*(567+8))^9$
-361363	$-1-(2+(3^4-5)^6)*789$	-419158	$-1+(2-3^4*(567+8))^9$
-361476	$(12+3^4*(5-67)*8)^9$	-419192	$1-(2+3^4*(567+8))^9$
-361692	$(-12+3^4*(5-67)*8)^9$	-419194	$-1-(2+3^4*(567+8))^9$
-362124	$(12-(3^4+5)^6*78)^9$	-419667	$(1+2)*(34-(5^6-78)*9)$
-366612	$12-(3^4-5)^6*78^9$	-419765	$-1-23^4-(5^6-78)^9$
-366636	$-12-(3^4-5)^6*78^9$	-419782	$1-2-3*(4+(5^6-78)*9)$
-366732	$(12+(3^4-5)^6*78)^9$	-419783	$1*-2-3*(4+(5^6-78)*9)$
-367390	$1+(2-3^4*567)*8+9$	-420327	$(1+2)*(3^4-(5^6-7^8)*9)$
-367442	$-1-(2+3^4*567)*8-9$	-420375	$(1-2)*3*(4+(5^6-7^8)*9)$
-368622	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6-7-8-9)$	-421167	$1-23^4-(5^6+78)^9$
-368658	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6-7-8-9)$	-421169	$-1-23^4-(5^6+78)^9$
-370063	$-1-((2^3)^4-5+67)*89$	-423351	$(1+2)*(3^4-(5^6+7^8)*9)$
-372861	$(1+2)*((3^4-5^6+7)*8+9)$	-423375	$1^2*3*(4-(5^6+7^8)*9)$
-372915	$(1+2)*((3^4-5^6+7)*8-9)$	-423399	$(1-2)*3*(4+(5^6+7^8)*9)$
-374562	$(1+2)*(3^4-(5^6-7)*8+9)$	-423423	$(1+2)*(3^4-(5^6+7^8)*9)$
-375438	$(-1-2)*(3^4+(5^6+7)*8+9)$	-423879	$(1+2)*(34-(5^6+78)*9)$
-376803	$(-1-2)*((3^4+5^6-7)*8+9)$	-423957	$12+3*(4-(5^6+78)*9)$
-377085	$(-1-2)*((3^4+5^6+7)*8-9)$	-424083	$(-1-2)*(34+(5^6+78)*9)$
-377139	$(-1-2)*((3^4+5^6+7)*8+9)$	-426708	$-12*((3^4-5)^6*78-9)$
-377199	$(1+(2-3^4*5)^6*(6+7)*8)^9$	-426924	$-12*((3^4-5)^6*78+9)$
-377217	$(-1+(2-3^4*5)^6*(6+7)*8)^9$	-435416	$12^3-4*(5^6*7-89)$
-378927	$(1+(2-3^4*5)^6*(6+7)*8)^9$	-436128	$12^3-4*(5^6*7+89)$
-378945	$(-1+(2-3^4*5)^6*(6+7)*8)^9$	-437108	$12^3-4*(5^6*7-89)$
-379233	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^6*(6+7)*8)^9$	-437120	$1+23-4*(5^6*7-89)$
-380943	$(1-(2+3^4*5)^6*(6+7)*8)^9$	-437121	$1*23-4*(5^6*7-89)$
-380961	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^6*(6+7)*8)^9$	-437122	$-1+23-4*(5^6*7-89)$
-381111	$-12*(3^4*5^6*7+8)+9$	-437129	$12+3-4*(5^6*7-89)$
-381129	$-12*(3^4*5^6*7+8)-9$	-437166	$1-23-4*(5^6*7-89)$
-381996	$-12*3^4*(56*7-8+9)$	-437168	$-1-23-4*(5^6*7-89)$
-382812	$1/2*((-3-4)^5*5^6*7-8+9)$	-437180	$-12*3-4*(5^6*7-89)$
-384019	$(1+2*3^4*5^6)*(-7-8^9)$	-437188	$1+23-4*(5^6*7-8^9)$
-387111	$-12+3^4*(5-67*8)^9$	-437197	$12+3-4*(5^6*7-8^9)$
-388692	$-12*(3^4*(56*7+8)-9)$	-437209	$(-1+2)*3-4*(5^6*7-8^9)$
-390327	$12+3^4*(5-67*8)^9$	-437791	$1^2*3-4*(5^6*7+8^9)$
-390351	$-12+3^4*(5-67*8)^9$	-437820	$12^3-4*(5^6*7+89)$
-391137	$12-3^4*(5+67*8)^9$	-437832	$1+23-4*(5^6*7+89)$
-394281	$(12-3^4*(5+67*8))^9$	-437834	$-1+23-4*(5^6*7+89)$
-394377	$12-3^4*(5+67*8)^9$	-437871	$-12-3-4*(5^6*7+89)$
-394401	$-12-3^4*(5+67*8)^9$	-437878	$1-23-4*(5^6*7+89)$
-394497	$(12+3^4*(5+67*8))^9$	-437879	$-1*23-4*(5^6*7+89)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-437892	$-12 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 89)$	-497909	$1 \cdot -2 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 678) \cdot 9$
-438872	$-12^{\wedge} 3 \cdot 4 \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 - 89)$	-497910	$-1 \cdot -2 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 678) \cdot 9$
-439584	$-12^{\wedge} 3 \cdot 4 \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 89)$	-497924	$1 \cdot (2 + 3^4 \cdot (5 + 678)) \cdot 9$
-448911	$(1 + (2 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6) \cdot 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	-501423	$(-1 \cdot 2 / (3 / (4 \cdot 5))) \cdot (6^{\wedge} 7 / 8 - 9)$
-448929	$(-1 + (2 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6) \cdot 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	-504999	$(1 \cdot (2 / 3^{\wedge} 4 - 5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8) \cdot 9$
-449199	$(1 \cdot (2 + 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6) \cdot 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	-505017	$(1 + (2 \cdot 3^4 + 5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8) \cdot -9$
-449217	$(1 + (2 + 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6) \cdot 7) \cdot 8) \cdot -9$	-507772	$1/2 \cdot (3^4 + 5 \cdot 6 \cdot (7 - 8 \cdot 9))$
-450063	$(1 \cdot (2 + 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6)) \cdot 7 \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	-507853	$-1/2 \cdot (3^4 + 5 \cdot 6 \cdot (7 \cdot 8 + 9))$
-450550	$(-1 + (2^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 4 \cdot (5 + 6)) \cdot (7 - 8 - 9)$	-508272	$(1 + (2 \cdot 3^4) \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7) / (8 + 9)$
-450570	$(1 + (2^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 4 \cdot (5 + 6)) \cdot (7 - 8 - 9)$	-511975	$(1 \cdot (2^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 4 \cdot 5) \cdot (6 \cdot 7 - 8 - 9)$
-451971	$(1 \cdot 2 / (3^{\wedge} 4 - 5)) \cdot (6 + 7 \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	-512025	$(1 + (2^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 4 \cdot 5) \cdot (-6 \cdot 7 + 8 + 9)$
-451989	$(1 + 2 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot (6 + 7 \cdot 8)) \cdot -9$	-512244	$-12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6 \cdot (78 + 9))$
-453011	$-1 + (2 \cdot (3^4 - 5) \cdot 67) \cdot 89$	-512995	$1 \cdot (2 + (3^4 + 5) \cdot 67) \cdot 89$
-453365	$1 \cdot (2 + (3^4 - 5) \cdot 67) \cdot 89$	-512997	$-1 \cdot (2 + (3^4 + 5) \cdot 67) \cdot 89$
-453367	$-1 \cdot (2 + (3^4 - 5) \cdot 67) \cdot 89$	-519954	$(1 - 23/4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 89)$
-455129	$1 \cdot 234 \cdot ((5^6 + 7) / 8 - 9)$	-523557	$(1 + 2) \cdot ((3^{\wedge} 4 - 5) \cdot 6^{\wedge} 7 / 8 + 9)$
-455131	$-1 \cdot 234 \cdot ((5^6 + 7) / 8 - 9)$	-524753	$1 + (2 \cdot (3^4 + 5) \cdot 678) \cdot 9$
-457075	$(-1 \cdot 234) \cdot ((5^6 + 7) / 8 - 9)$	-526149	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot ((3^{\wedge} 4 - 5) \cdot 6^{\wedge} 7 / 8 - 9)$
-457226	$1 \cdot 234 \cdot (5^6 + 7) / 8 + 9$	-526203	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot ((3^{\wedge} 4 - 5) \cdot 6^{\wedge} 7 / 8 + 9)$
-457228	$-1 \cdot 234 \cdot (5^6 + 7) / 8 + 9$	-538623	$1 \cdot 2^{\wedge} (3 + 4 + 5) / 6 \cdot 789$
-457244	$1 \cdot 234 \cdot (5^6 + 7) / 8 - 9$	-538625	$-1 \cdot 2^{\wedge} (3 + 4 + 5) / 6 \cdot 789$
-457246	$-1 \cdot 234 \cdot (5^6 + 7) / 8 - 9$	-539772	$12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot (8 + 9)$
-457379	$(1 \cdot 234) \cdot ((5^6 + 7) / 8 + 9)$	-539796	$-12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot (8 + 9)$
-459341	$1 \cdot 234 \cdot ((5^6 + 7) / 8 + 9)$	-541655	$12 \cdot (3 + 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 78) / 9$
-459343	$-1 \cdot 234 \cdot ((5^6 + 7) / 8 + 9)$	-541679	$-12 \cdot (3 + 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 78) / 9$
-459639	$(1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3^4 - 5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	-549163	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 78 - 9)$
-459657	$(1 + 2 \cdot (3^4 - 5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8) \cdot -9$	-549197	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 78 + 9)$
-461305	$(-1 \cdot 234) \cdot ((5^6 + 7) / 8 + 9)$	-549199	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 78 + 9)$
-461499	$(12 + 3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 67) \cdot (-8 - 9)$	-554025	$(12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6) \cdot 7) \cdot 89$
-463735	$-1 + (2 \cdot (3^4 - 5) \cdot 678) \cdot 9$	-555081	$12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6) \cdot 7 \cdot 89$
-463769	$1 \cdot (2 + (3^4 - 5) \cdot 678) \cdot 9$	-555105	$-12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6) \cdot 7 \cdot 89$
-463771	$-1 \cdot (2 + (3^4 - 5) \cdot 678) \cdot 9$	-556161	$(12 + 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6) \cdot 7) \cdot -89$
-466494	$1 \cdot (23^4 + 56) \cdot (7 + 8) / 9$	-558883	$1 + 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6^{\wedge} 7 + 89)$
-466496	$-1 \cdot (23^4 + 56) \cdot (7 + 8) / 9$	-558885	$-1 + 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6^{\wedge} 7 + 89)$
-467517	$(12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot (6 + 7)) \cdot 89$	-559239	$1 + 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6^{\wedge} 7 - 89)$
-468835	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot (34 + 5 \cdot 6 \cdot (7 + 8) + 9)$	-559241	$-1 + 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6^{\wedge} 7 - 89)$
-468837	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot (34 + 5 \cdot 6 \cdot (7 + 8) + 9)$	-560503	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 + 6^{\wedge} 7 - 89)$
-469653	$(12 + 3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot (6 + 7)) \cdot -89$	-560505	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 + 6^{\wedge} 7 - 89)$
-470569	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot ((3 + 4)^{\wedge} 5 / (6 / 7 / 8) - 9)$	-560859	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 + 6^{\wedge} 7 + 89)$
-470623	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot ((3 + 4)^{\wedge} 5 / (6 / 7 / 8) + 9)$	-560861	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 + 6^{\wedge} 7 + 89)$
-474759	$(1 \cdot (2 / 3^{\wedge} 4 - 5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	-561420	$-12^{\wedge} 3 \cdot 4 \cdot (5^6 - 78) \cdot 9$
-474777	$(1 + (2 \cdot 3^4 - 5) \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8) \cdot -9$	-563179	$1 \cdot 23 \cdot (4 \cdot 5^6 + 78) \cdot 9$
-474795	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot (3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7) / 8 - 9)$	-563180	$-1 + 23 \cdot (4 \cdot 5^6 + 78) \cdot 9$
-474849	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot (3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7) / 8 + 9)$	-563224	$1 \cdot 23 \cdot (4 \cdot 5^6 + 78) \cdot 9$
-482004	$12 \cdot (3^4 \cdot (5 - 67) \cdot 8 + 9)$	-563225	$1 \cdot 23 \cdot (4 \cdot 5^6 + 78) \cdot 9$
-482220	$12 \cdot (3^4 \cdot (5 - 67) \cdot 8 - 9)$	-563580	$12^{\wedge} 3 \cdot 4 \cdot (5^6 + 78) \cdot 9$
-482589	$(1 + 2 / (3^{\wedge} 4 - 4 / (5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8))) \cdot 9$	-564930	$-12^{\wedge} 3 \cdot 4 \cdot (5^6 + 78) \cdot 9$
-482607	$(-1 + 2 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8)) \cdot 9$	-573648	$-12 \cdot (3^4 - 5) \cdot (6 + 7 \cdot 89)$
-486109	$(-1 + (2 + 3) \cdot (4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8)) / 9$	-583412	$-12 \cdot (3 + 4 \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 8) / 9)$
-490598	$1 + (2 + 3^4 \cdot (5 - 678)) \cdot 9$	-583671	$(1 \cdot (2^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 4 \cdot (5 / 6 + 7 + 8)) \cdot 9$
-490600	$-1 + (2 + 3^4 \cdot (5 - 678)) \cdot 9$	-583689	$(1 + (2^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 4 \cdot (5 / 6 + 7 + 8)) \cdot -9$
-490614	$1 + 2 + 3^4 \cdot (5 - 678) \cdot 9$	-592918	$(1 \cdot (23^4 + 5) / 6 / 7) \cdot 89$
-490615	$1 \cdot 2 + 3^4 \cdot (5 - 678) \cdot 9$	-612348	$12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot (7 + 8) \cdot 9$
-490616	$1 \cdot 2 + 3^4 \cdot (5 - 678) \cdot 9$	-612372	$-12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot (7 + 8) \cdot 9$
-490618	$1 \cdot 2 + 3^4 \cdot (5 - 678) \cdot 9$	-614370	$(1 \cdot (2^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 4 \cdot 5) \cdot (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
-490619	$-1 \cdot 2 + 3^4 \cdot (5 - 678) \cdot 9$	-614430	$(1 + (2^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 4 \cdot 5) \cdot (-6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$
-490620	$-1 \cdot 2 + 3^4 \cdot (5 - 678) \cdot 9$	-616248	$-12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6 + 7 \cdot 89)$
-490634	$1 \cdot (2 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 - 678)) \cdot 9$	-619786	$(1 + 2 / 3 + 4) \cdot (5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 - 8 + 9)$
-490636	$-1 \cdot (2 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 - 678)) \cdot 9$	-619888	$(1 + 2 / 3 + 4) \cdot (5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 - 8 - 9)$
-491508	$-12 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 + 7 + 8) \cdot 9$	-622557	$(1 + 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6^{\wedge} 7 / 8)) \cdot 9$
-492132	$1/2 \cdot (3 + (4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 + 8) \cdot 9)$	-622575	$(-1 + 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6^{\wedge} 7 / 8)) \cdot 9$
-492135	$1/2 \cdot (-3 + (4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 + 8) \cdot 9)$	-625374	$(12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6) \cdot 78) \cdot 9$
-492160	$1/2 + (3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 / 8) \cdot 9$	-625590	$(12 + 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6) \cdot 78) \cdot -9$
-492161	$-1/2 + (3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 / 8) \cdot 9$	-629417	$1 \cdot 23 / 4 \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 89)$
-492204	$1/2 \cdot (3 + (4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 - 8) \cdot 9)$	-629419	$-1 \cdot 23 / 4 \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 89)$
-492207	$1/2 \cdot (-3 + (4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 - 8) \cdot 9)$	-629676	$(1 + 2 \cdot (3^4 - 5 \cdot 6^{\wedge} 7) / 8) \cdot 9$
-492214	$1/2 \cdot (3 + 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 / 8) \cdot 9$	-630036	$(-1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3^4 - 5 + 6^{\wedge} 7) / 8) \cdot 9$
-492215	$1/2 \cdot (3 + 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 / 8) \cdot 9$	-637137	$(1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 + 6^{\wedge} 7 / 8)) \cdot 9$
-492240	$1/2 \cdot (3 \cdot (4 + 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 + 8) \cdot 9)$	-637155	$(-1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 + 6^{\wedge} 7 / 8)) \cdot 9$
-492243	$-1/2 \cdot (3 \cdot (4 + 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 + 8) \cdot 9)$	-640642	$1/2 \cdot (3 \cdot (4 + 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 + 8) \cdot 9)$
-497906	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 678) \cdot 9$	-645000	$(1 + 2 / 3) \cdot (4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 - 8) \cdot 9$
-497908	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 678) \cdot 9$	-650469	$(1 \cdot (2^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 4 / 5) \cdot (6 + 789)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-652059	$(1+(2^3)^4/5)^*(-6-789)$	-841239	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5+6^7+8^9)$
-655854	$-12*(3+4*(5^6*7/8-9))$	-843869	$(1-23)^4-5^6*(78-9)$
-656097	$-1-2*(3*(4+5^6*7)-89)$	-849920	$(1+2/3)/(4^8-5/(6-7*8^9))$
-656222	$(1+2^3)^*(4-5^6*(7+8-9))$	-854163	$1+2/3*(4+5^6*(7-89))$
-656278	$(1-2^3)^*(4+5^6*(7+8-9))$	-870816	$(1-2^3*4^5*6)^*(7+89)$
-660299	$(1+23^4*5^6*7)/-89$	-871008	$(-1-2^3*4^5*6)^*(7+89)$
-666404	$-12*(3+4*(5^6-7)*8/9)$	-874283	$-1+2*(3-4*(5^6*7-89))$
-687624	$(1-2^3/4^8-5/6)^*7*8^9$	-874293	$1-2*(3+4*(5^6*7-89))$
-688632	$(1+2^3/4^8-5/6)^*7*8^9$	-874573	$(1-2^3)^*(4+(5^6-7)*8-9)$
-694984	$1/2*(34-(5^6-7)*89)$	-874643	$(1+2^3)^*(4-(5^6-7)*8-9)$
-695018	$-1/2*(34+(5^6-7)*89)$	-874699	$(1-2^3)^*(4+(5^6-7)*8+9)$
-695607	$1/2*(34-(5^6+7)*89)$	-875301	$(1+2^3)^*(4-(5^6+7)*8+9)$
-695641	$-1/2*(34+(5^6+7)*89)$	-875357	$(1-2^3)^*(4+(5^6+7)*8-9)$
-699507	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5^6)^*(7+8)-9)$	-875427	$(1+2^3)^*(4-(5^6+7)*8-9)$
-699634	$1-(2+3)^*(4+(5^6-78)*9)$	-875707	$-1+2*(3-4*(5^6*7+89))$
-706654	$1-(2+3)^*(4+(5^6+78)*9)$	-875717	$1-2*(3+4*(5^6*7+89))$
-706743	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5^6)^*(7+8)-9)$	-880597	$(1-(2^3)^4*5)^*(6^7-8+9)$
-707965	$(1+2/3+4)^*((-5^6+7)*8+9)$	-880683	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(-6^7+8-9)$
-708067	$(1+2/3+4)^*((-5^6+7)*8-9)$	-889287	$(1-2^3)^*(4*(5^6+7)/8)/9$
-711504	$-12/3^4-4*(5^6+78^9)$	-905199	$(1-2^3)^*(3+4+5)^*(6+7)^*(8+9)$
-718779	$(1-2*(3^4-5)^*6)^*789$	-905233	$(1+2^3)^*(3+4+5)^*(6+7)^*(8-9)$
-720617	$(1+2^3-3)^*(-4-5-6-7^8/9)$	-906287	$(1-2*(3^4-5)^*6)^*789$
-729093	$1-2*(3+4^8(5-6+7)*89)$	-906465	$(-1-2*(3^4-5)^*6)^*789$
-729165	$(1+2/3)^*(-4/(5^6-6/7)-8+9)$	-923916	$-12*(3^4*5^6-7)^*(8+9)$
-729195	$(1+2/3)^*(-4/(5^6-6/7)-8-9)$	-924868	$1/(2/((3^4-5^6)^*7))^*(8+9)$
-733617	$(1+2)^*3^4*(5-6^7*8^9)$	-926772	$-12*(3^4*5^6+7)^*(8+9)$
-734813	$1-2*(3^4*5^6*7^8-9)$	-927513	$(-1-2*(3^4-5)^*6)^*789$
-734851	$-1-2*(3^4*5^6*7^8+9)$	-929647	$1/2*(3^4-5^6*7^8(8+9))$
-736047	$(1+2)^*-3^4*(5+6^7*8^9)$	-929720	$1/2*(3-(4+5^6*7)^*(8+9))$
-743822	$(-1+2^3*4^5*6)^*(7-89)$	-929723	$-1/2*(3+(4+5^6*7)^*(8+9))$
-745281	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5-6^7*8^9)$	-936102	$(1-(2^3*4^5)^*6)^*789$
-747711	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5+6^7*8^9)$	-949474	$(1+23)^4+5^6*(7-89)$
-749933	$-1+2*(34-5^6*(7+8+9))$	-976552	$1/2*(3^4-5^6(6+7+8)+9)$
-749983	$1/2*(34-5^6*(7+89))$	-976573	$1/2*(3^4-5^6(6+7+8)-9)$
-750017	$1/-2*(34+5^6*(7+89))$	-976765	$1/2*(3^4*5-6(6+7-8)^9)$
-750067	$1-2*(34+5^6*(7+8+9))$	-979449	$12-(3+4)^*(5^6-78)^9$
-753870	$1-23*(4^8(5-6+7)*8+9)$	-979473	$-12-(3+4)^*(5^6-78)^9$
-764990	$12-(3+4)^*(5^6*7-89)$	-980819	$(1-2^3)^*(-4+(5^6-7^8)*9)$
-765014	$-12-(3+4)^*(5^6*7-89)$	-980875	$(1-2^3)^*(4+(5^6-7^8)*9)$
-765093	$(1-2^3)^*(-4+5^6*7-8^9)$	-981243	$(-1+2^3*4^5)^*(5-678)^9$
-765149	$(1-2^3)^*(4+5^6*7-8^9)$	-983402	$(1+2^3)^*(4-(5^6-7-8)^9)$
-765478	$(1+2^3)^*(4-5^6*7+8+9)$	-983458	$(1-2^3)^*(4+(5^6-7-8)^9)$
-765772	$(1-2^3)^*(4+5^6*7+8+9)$	-983661	$12-((3+4)^*5^6-78)^9$
-766101	$(1-2^3)^*(-4+5^6*7+8^9)$	-983685	$-12-((3+4)^*5^6-78)^9$
-766157	$(1-2^3)^*(4+5^6*7+8^9)$	-984068	$1+234-(5^6*7-8)^9$
-766236	$12-(3+4)^*(5^6*7+89)$	-984070	$-1+234-(5^6*7-8)^9$
-766260	$-12-(3+4)^*(5^6*7+89)$	-984680	$1-234-(5^6*7+8)^9$
-777783	$(1-2*(3+4/5^6-6^7)*8)/9$	-984682	$-1-234-(5^6*7+8)^9$
-796275	$(1+2)^*(3^4-(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	-985065	$12-((3+4)^*5^6+78)^9$
-796542	$-12-3*(4+(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	-985089	$-12-((3+4)^*5^6+78)^9$
-796761	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	-985292	$(1+2^3)^*(4-(5^6+7+8)^9)$
-796989	$(1+2)^*(3^4-(5^6+7)^*(8+9))$	-985348	$(1-2^3)^*(4+(5^6+7+8)^9)$
-797268	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+(5^6+7)^*(8+9))$	-985443	$-12*(3/4*5^6*7+89)$
-797475	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+(5^6+7)^*(8+9))$	-987875	$(1-2^3)^*(-4+(5^6+7^8)*9)$
-798283	$1+23^4-5^6*(78-9)$	-987931	$(1-2^3)^*(4+(5^6+7^8)*9)$
-798284	$1^*23^4-5^6*(78-9)$	-989277	$12-(3+4)^*(5^6+78)^9$
-798285	$-1+23^4-5^6*(78-9)$	-989301	$-12-(3+4)^*(5^6+78)^9$
-806251	$(-1-2*(3^4*5^6-7))^*89$	-991185	$(1+2/3+4)^*5*(6^7/-8+9)$
-808565	$(1-2*(3^4*5^6+7))^*89$	-991695	$(1+2/3+4)^*-5*(6^7/8+9)$
-808743	$(-1-2*(3^4*5^6+7))^*89$	-995732	$(1-(2^3*4^5)^*6)^*789$
-809190	$1^2/(-3^4(-4-5)/(6^7-8/9))$	-995805	$(1-2^3*4^5(5+678))^9$
-812475	$1+2^3*(4-5^6*78/9)$	-995823	$(-1-2^3*4^5(5+678))^9$
-816372	$-12*(3^4*5^6*(7+8)-9)$	-995910	$(1+(2^3*4^5)^*6)^*789$
-816588	$-12*(3^4*5^6*(7+8)+9)$	-1027500	$(12+3)^4-5^6*(78-9)$
-838377	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5-6^7+8^9)$	-1027599	$(1+23)^4-5^6*(78+9)$
-838542	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5-6^7+8+9)$	-1043448	$-12-3/4*(5^6+7)^*89$
-838590	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5-6^7-8+9)$	-1069065	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5^6+7-8))^*-9$
-838596	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5-6^7+8-9)$	-1071213	$12^3*4-5^6*(78-9)$
-838644	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5-6^7-8-9)$	-1072524	$12+(3^4-5^6)^*(78-9)$
-840972	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5+6^7-8-9)$	-1072548	$-12+(3^4-5^6)^*(78-9)$
-841020	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5+6^7+8-9)$	-1073655	$(1-(2^3)^4*(5^6-7/8))^*9$
-841026	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5+6^7+8+9)$	-1073673	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5^6-7/8))^*-9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1076393	$12^{\wedge}3+4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1224567	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*5*6*7)*8)*9$
-1076401	$12^{\wedge}3-4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1224873	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4*5*6*7)*8)*-9$
-1077153	$12*3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1225719	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4*5*6)*7*8)*9$
-1077693	$12^{\wedge}3/4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1225737	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4*5*6)*7*8)*-9$
-1077981	$12*3*4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1228838	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6+7)/-8-9)$
-1078023	$(1+2)*34-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1230625	$(12+3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1078032	$1+23*4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1230759	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4*5)*6*7*8)*9$
-1078034	$-1+23*4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1230777	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4*5)*6*7*8)*-9$
-1078091	$1^{\wedge}2*34-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1239521	$(1+2/3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7))*8+9$
-1078108	$1/2*34-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1239555	$(-1+2/3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7))*8+9$
-1078142	$-1/2*34-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1244007	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*5/6^{\wedge}7)*8)*9$
-1078159	$1^{\wedge}2*-34-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1244025	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*5/6^{\wedge}7)*8)*9$
-1078213	$(1-23)*4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1244295	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4*5/6^{\wedge}7)*8)*9$
-1078216	$1-23*4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1244313	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4*5/6^{\wedge}7)*8)*-9$
-1078227	$(-1-2)*34-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1253359	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6+7))*8+9$
-1078557	$-12^{\wedge}3/4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1253393	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6+7))*(-8-9)$
-1079097	$-12*3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1257201	$-12*(3/4*5^{\wedge}6-78)*9$
-1079533	$1+23^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(78+9)$	-1258566	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-78-9)$
-1079534	$1*23^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(78+9)$	-1258590	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-78-9)$
-1079535	$-1+23^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(78+9)$	-1259286	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-78)+9$
-1079849	$-12^{\wedge}3+4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1259304	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-78)-9$
-1079857	$-12^{\wedge}3-4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1259328	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-78)-9$
-1081320	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6))*7+8+9$	-1260024	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-78+9)$
-1083702	$12-(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)*(78-9)$	-1260048	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-78+9)$
-1083726	$-12-(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)*(78-9)$	-1264957	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)+89$
-1085037	$-12^{\wedge}3*4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-1264981	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)+89$
-1085387	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)*(6+7*8-9)$	-1265135	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)-89$
-1085493	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)*(-6-7*8+9)$	-1265159	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)-89$
-1093778	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7-8-9))$	-1266091	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)+89$
-1102883	$(1-(23^{\wedge}4-5)*67)/(8+9)$	-1266115	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)+89$
-1119379	$-1+2*(3-4*(5^{\wedge}6-78)*9)$	-1266269	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)-89$
-1120000	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)/(4*5)^{\wedge}(6+7-8-9)$	-1266293	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)-89$
-1122389	$1+(234-(5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)*9$	-1271202	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+78-9)$
-1122391	$-1+(234-(5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)*9$	-1271226	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+78-9)$
-1123397	$1+(234-(5^{\wedge}6+7)*8)*9$	-1271922	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+78)+9$
-1123399	$-1+(234-(5^{\wedge}6+7)*8)*9$	-1271940	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+78)-9$
-1124972	$(1+2*3)*(4-5^{\wedge}6/(7/8/9))$	-1271964	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+78)-9$
-1125028	$(-1-2*3)*(4+5^{\wedge}6/(7/8/9))$	-1272660	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+78+9)$
-1125119	$(1-23)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(78+9)$	-1272684	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+78+9)$
-1126601	$1-(234+(5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)*9$	-1272700	$12*(3-4^{\wedge}5/(6/7))*89$
-1126603	$-1-(234+(5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)*9$	-1274596	$12-(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)*(7-89)$
-1127609	$1-(234+(5^{\wedge}6+7)*8)*9$	-1274620	$-12-(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)*7-89$
-1127611	$-1-(234+(5^{\wedge}6+7)*8)*9$	-1279108	$-12*(3+4^{\wedge}5/(6/7))*89$
-1130583	$1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+78)*9)$	-1280527	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6-7^{\wedge}8))/9$
-1130585	$-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+78)*9)$	-1280818	$12^{\wedge}3/4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1130647	$1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+78)*9)$	-1280869	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8))/9$
-1130649	$-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+78)*9)$	-1281052	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5/6-7^{\wedge}8))/9$
-1138167	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5*6+7/8))*9$	-1281148	$(1+2)*34+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1138185	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5*6+7/8))*-9$	-1281162	$(-1+23)*4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1142775	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5*6-7+8))*9$	-1281190	$(12+3)*4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1142793	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5*6-7+8))*-9$	-1281216	$1^{\wedge}2*34+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1155025	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3+4+5)*6)*(7*8-9)$	-1281233	$1/2*34+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1155119	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4+5)*6)*(-7*8+9)$	-1281267	$-1/2*34+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1166665	$(-1+(2-3*4/5^{\wedge}6-6*7)*8)/9$	-1281284	$1^{\wedge}2*-34+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1168224	$(1+23)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+89)$	-1281310	$(-12-3)*4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1185209	$(1+23^{\wedge}4*(5+67))/(-8-9)$	-1281338	$(1-23)*4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1201713	$1+2-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-789)$	-1281352	$(-1-2)*34+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1201714	$1-2-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-789)$	-1281394	$-12*3*4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1201715	$1^{\wedge}2-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-789)$	-1281607	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6+7^{\wedge}8))/9$
-1201717	$1-2-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-789)$	-1281682	$12^{\wedge}3/-4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-1201718	$-1*2-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-789)$	-1287880	$12+(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)*(7-89)$
-1201719	$-1-2-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-789)$	-1287904	$-12+(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)*(7-89)$
-1208261	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)*(6*7+8+9)$	-1304628	$12*((3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)*7+89)$
-1208379	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)*(6-7*8-9)$	-1306764	$12*((3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)*7-89)$
-1208751	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-78*9)$	-1308750	$(12+3)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(78+9)$
-1215150	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7*89)$	-1310460	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$
-1215174	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7*89)$	-1311439	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7)+89$
-1217570	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6+7)/-8+9)$	-1311617	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7)-89$
-1223645	$(1+2/3)*(4-5^{\wedge}6)*7*8-9$	-1312245	$-12-3*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$
-1223703	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*5*6)*7*8)*9$	-1312267	$12*(3*4-5^{\wedge}6*7)+89$
-1223721	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*5*6)*7*8)*9$	-1312275	$(1+2)*(3-4/5^{\wedge}6-6*7+8*9)$
-1223965	$(-1-2/3)*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7*8-9))$	-1312377	$1^{\wedge}2*3*(4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)+9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1312445	$12^*(3^4-5^6*7)-89$	-1423179	$(1+(2-3^4*(5^6-7))/8)^*9$
-1312555	$-12^*(3^4+5^6*7)+89$	-1423197	$(-1+(2-3^4*(5^6-7))/8)^*9$
-1312623	$1^2*-3^*(4*(5^6*7+8)+9)$	-1449375	$(12+3)^4-5^6*(7+89)$
-1312725	$(-1-2)^*(3+4^5*5^6*7+8^9)$	-1454009	$(1-(2^3)^4*5)^*(6+7^8+9)$
-1312733	$-12^*(3^4+5^6*7)-89$	-1454151	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(-6-7^8-9)$
-1313383	$-12^*(3^4+5^6*7)+89$	-1459629	$(1-(2+3^4)^*(5^6+7)/8)^*9$
-1313561	$-12^*(3^4+5^6*7)-89$	-1459647	$(1+(2+3^4)^*(5^6+7)/8)^*-9$
-1314540	$-12^*(3^4+5^6*7+89)$	-1468681	$1+2^*(34-5^6*(7^8-9))$
-1316076	$12-3^4*(5^6+7^8+9)$	-1468683	$-1+2^*(34-5^6*(7^8-9))$
-1316100	$-12-3^4*(5^6+7^8+9)$	-1468817	$1-2^*(34+5^6*(7^8-9))$
-1318236	$-12^*((3^4+5^6)^*7-89)$	-1468819	$-1-2^*(34+5^6*(7^8-9))$
-1320372	$-12^*((3^4+5^6)^*7+89)$	-1471527	$(1-((2^3)^4*5-6^*7)^*8)^*9$
-1322475	$12-3^4*(5^6+7^8+9)$	-1471545	$(1+((2^3)^4*5-6^*7)^*8)^*-9$
-1322499	$-12-3^4*(5^6+7^8+9)$	-1477575	$(1-((2^3)^4*5+6^*7)^*8)^*9$
-1329531	$1+2-3^4*(5^6+7^8+9)$	-1492212	$12+(3^4-5^6)^*(7+89)$
-1329532	$1^*2-3^4*(5^6+7^8+9)$	-1494967	$(-1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6-7-8^*9)$
-1329533	$1^2-3^4*(5^6+7^8+9)$	-1495113	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6-7-8^*9)$
-1329535	$1-2-3^4*(5^6+7^8+9)$	-1499301	$1^2*3^*(4^*(5^6+7)^*8+9)$
-1329536	$-1^*2-3^4*(5^6+7^8+9)$	-1499355	$1^2*3^*(4^*(-5^6+7)^*8-9)$
-1329537	$-1-2-3^4*(5^6+7^8+9)$	-1499796	$(1+2)^*(3-(4^5*5^6-7)^*8+9)$
-1352316	$12+(3^4-5^6)^*(7^8+9)$	-1499898	$(1+2)^*34-5^6*(7+89)$
-1352340	$-12+(3^4-5^6)^*(7^8+9)$	-1499912	$(-1+23)^4-5^6*(7+89)$
-1352463	$12^3*4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1499966	$1^2*34-5^6*(7+89)$
-1356800	$(-1-2/3)/(4^5-5/(6+7^8+9))$	-1500034	$1^2*-34-5^6*(7+89)$
-1357643	$12^3*4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1500088	$(1-23)^4-5^6*(7+89)$
-1357651	$12^3-4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1500102	$(-1-2)^*34-5^6*(7+89)$
-1357965	$1-23^4-5^6*(7^8-9)$	-1500204	$(-1-2)^*(3+(4^5*5^6+7)^*8+9)$
-1357966	$-1^*23^4-5^6*(7^8-9)$	-1500645	$1^2*3^*(4^*(5^6+7)^*8+9)$
-1357967	$-1-23^4-5^6*(7^8-9)$	-1500699	$1^2*-3^*(4^*(5^6+7)^*8+9)$
-1358943	$12^3/4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1507764	$12-(3^4+5^6)^*(7+89)$
-1359231	$12^*3^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1507788	$-12-(3^4+5^6)^*(7+89)$
-1359273	$(1+2)^*34-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1536852	$(12-3^4-4^5*6^7)^*89$
-1359279	$(1+23)^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1537908	$12+3^4-4^5-5^6*7^8+9$
-1359282	$1+23^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1537932	$-12+3^4-4^5-5^6*7^8+9$
-1359283	$1^*23^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1538988	$(12+3^4-4^5*6^7)^*-89$
-1359284	$-1^*23^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1561501	$(1-2^*3^4*567)^*(8+9)$
-1359315	$(12+3)^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1561535	$(-1-2^*3^4*567)^*(8+9)$
-1359341	$1^2*34-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1562317	$(-1-2^*(3^4*5^6+7^8))/9$
-1359358	$1/2^*34-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1574172	$(1-(23^4*5+67)/8)^*9$
-1359392	$-1/2^*34-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1574190	$(1+(23^4*5+67)/8)^*-9$
-1359409	$1^2*-34-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1597375	$(1-2^*(3+4+5)^*6)^*(7^8+9)$
-1359435	$(-12-3)^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1597505	$(1+2^*(3+4+5)^*6)^*(7-8^*9)$
-1359466	$1-23^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1624028	$12^*(3^4-5^6*7^8/9)$
-1359467	$1^*23^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1624856	$12^*(3^4-5^6*7^8/9)$
-1359468	$-1-23^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1624892	$12^*(3^4-5^6*7^8/9)$
-1359471	$(1+23)^*4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1624916	$12^*(3+4-5^6*7^8/9)$
-1359477	$(-1-2)^*34-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1624984	$12^*(3^4-5^6*7^8/9)$
-1359519	$12^*3^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1625016	$-12^*(3^4+5^6*7^8)/9$
-1359807	$-12^3/4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1625084	$-12^*(3+4+5^6*7^8/9)$
-1360347	$-12^*3^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1625108	$12^*(3^4+5^6*7^8)/-9$
-1361099	$-12^3+4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1625144	$-12^*(3^4+5^6*7^8/9)$
-1361107	$-12^3-4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1625972	$-12^*(3^4+5^6*7^8/9)$
-1366287	$-12^3*4-5^6*(7^8+9)$	-1639215	$1-23^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$
-1366410	$12-(3^4+5^6)^*(7^8+9)$	-1639216	$-1^*23^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$
-1366434	$-12-(3^4+5^6)^*(7^8+9)$	-1639217	$-1-23^4-5^6*(7^8+9)$
-1370880	$12^3(3-4+5)^*(-6+7+8/9)$	-1639230	$(12+3)^*(4-5^6*7+89)$
-1389285	$(1+(2-3^4)^*(5^6+7)/8)^*9$	-1639350	$(-12-3)^*(4+5^6*7-89)$
-1389303	$(-1+(2-3^4)^*(5^6+7)/8)^*9$	-1640534	$(1+2^*3)^*(4-5^6*(7+8)+9)$
-1395666	$(-12-3/4)^*(5^6*7+89)$	-1640590	$(1-2^3)^*(4+5^6*(7+8)-9)$
-1396123	$12+(3^4-4-5)^*6^7+89$	-1640660	$(1+2^*3)^*(4-5^6*(7+8)-9)$
-1396147	$-12+(3^4-4-5)^*6^7+89$	-1640716	$(1-2^3)^*(4+5^6*(7+8)+9)$
-1396301	$12+(3^4-4-5)^*6^7-89$	-1641900	$(12+3)^*(4-5^6*7-89)$
-1396325	$-12+(3^4-4-5)^*6^7-89$	-1642020	$(-12-3)^*(4+5^6*7+89)$
-1403035	$12-(3^4-4+5)^*6^7+89$	-1678932	$12^*(3^4-(5^6-78)^*9)$
-1403059	$-12-(3^4-4+5)^*6^7+89$	-1685406	$-12-3^*(4^5*5^6-78)^*9$
-1403213	$12-(3^4-4+5)^*6^7-89$	-1686483	$(1-2^*(3/4/5^6-6-7)^*8)^*9$
-1403237	$-12-(3^4-4+5)^*6^7-89$	-1686786	$12-(3^4*5^6-78)^*9$
-1405209	$(1-2^*3^4*(5+6))^*789$	-1686810	$-12-(3^4*5^6-78)^*9$
-1406787	$(-1-2^*3^4*(5+6))^*789$	-1688214	$-12-(3^4*5^6+78)^*9$
-1407744	$12^3(3-4+5)^*(-6+7-8/9)$	-1688517	$(-1-2^*(3/4/5^6-6+7)^*8)^*9$
-1411635	$(1+(2-(3+4)^5/(6/7))^*8)^*9$	-1689594	$12-3^*(4^5*5^6+78)^*9$
-1411941	$(1+(2+(3+4)^5/(6/7))^*8)^*-9$	-1689618	$-12-3^*(4^5*5^6+78)^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1695780	$12^*(3^4-(5^6+78)^9)$	-2156087	$1+2^*(3^4-5^6*(78-9))$
-1695840	$12^*(3+4-(5^6+78)^9)$	-2156089	$-1+2^*(3^4-5^6*(78-9))$
-1695912	$12-3^4*(5^6+78)^9$	-2156157	$1+23^*(4-5^6*(7+8-9))$
-1695936	$-12-3^4*(5^6+78)^9$	-2156159	$-1+23^*(4-5^6*(7+8-9))$
-1696008	$-12^*(3+4+(5^6+78)^9)$	-2156182	$1^2*(34-5^6*(78-9))$
-1696068	$-12^*(3^4+(5^6+78)^9)$	-2156183	$-1+2^*(34-5^6*(78-9))$
-1719816	$(1-(2^3)^4*5/6)^{7*8*9}$	-2156263	$1-2^*(3+4+5^6*(78-9))$
-1720824	$(1+(2^3)^4*5/6)^{7*8*9}$	-2156317	$1-2^*(34+5^6*(78-9))$
-1740715	$(1-(2^3)^4*5)^*(6+7+8^9)$	-2156318	$-1^2*(34+5^6*(78-9))$
-1740885	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(-6-7-8^9)$	-2156341	$1-23^*(4+5^6*(7+8-9))$
-1793589	$(-1-2)^*((3^4(4^5-6)+7)/8-9)$	-2156343	$-1-23^*(4+5^6*(7+8-9))$
-1793643	$(-1-2)^*((3^4(4^5-6)+7)/8+9)$	-2156411	$1-2^*(3^4+5^6*(78-9))$
-1840080	$(1+(2/3^4-4-5^6)^7)^*(8+9)$	-2156413	$-1-2^*(3^4+5^6*(78-9))$
-1840114	$(-1+(2^3)^4-5^6)^7*(8+9)$	-2176541	$(1+23^4*(5-67-8))/9$
-1858514	$(1+2^3)^*(4-(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	-2202882	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6*(7^8-9))$
-1858570	$(1-2^3)^*(4+(5^6-7)^*(8+9))$	-2203089	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6*(7^8-9))$
-1860180	$(1+2^3)^*(4-(5^6+7)^*(8+9))$	-2203101	$12+3^*(4-5^6*(7^8-9))$
-1860236	$(1-2^3)^*(4+(5^6+7)^*(8+9))$	-2203113	$1^2*3^*(4-5^6*(7^8-9))$
-1878636	$(1-(2^3)^4+5^6)^7*(8+9)$	-2203137	$(1-2)^*3^*(4+5^6*(7^8-9))$
-1878670	$(1+(2^3)^4+5^6)^7*(-8-9)$	-2203149	$-12-3^*(4+5^6*(7^8-9))$
-1916149	$(1+2)^*(3^4+(5^6-7^8)/9)$	-2203161	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6*(7^8-9))$
-1916356	$(1-2)^*(3^4+(5^6-7^8)/9)$	-2203368	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+5^6*(7^8-9))$
-1916368	$12+3^*(4+(5^6-7^8)/9)$	-2218176	$-12^3*(4^5/(6/7)+89)$
-1916416	$-12-3^*(4-(5^6-7^8)/9)$	-2247525	$(1+2^*(3^4-(5^6-7)^8))^9$
-1916428	$(1+2)^*(-3^4+(5^6-7^8)/9)$	-2248965	$(1-2^*(3-4+(5^6-7)^8))^9$
-1916635	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-(5^6-7^8)/9)$	-2249019	$(-1+2^*(3-4-(5^6-7)^8))^9$
-1941425	$(1-2^3)^*(3+4+5)^6*(7+8^9)$	-2249541	$(1+2^*(3^4-(5^6+7)^8))^9$
-1941583	$(1+2^3)^*(3+4+5)^6*(-7-8^9)$	-2249559	$(-1+2^*(3^4-(5^6+7)^8))^9$
-1945505	$(1-(2^3)^4*5)^*((6+7)^8-9)$	-2250441	$(1-2^*(3^4+(5^6-7)^8))^9$
-1945695	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*((-6-7)^8+9)$	-2250459	$(-1-2^*(3^4+(5^6-7)^8))^9$
-1967139	$(1+2^*(3^4-5^6*7+8))^9$	-2250783	$(1+2^*(3^4-(5^6+7)^8))^9$
-1967427	$(1+2^*(3^4-5^6*7-8))^9$	-2250801	$(-1+2^*(3^4-(5^6+7)^8))^9$
-1967445	$(-1+2^*(3^4-5^6*7-8))^9$	-2250981	$(1-2^*(3-4+(5^6+7)^8))^9$
-1968399	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-5^6*7+8)^9$	-2251035	$(-1+2^*(3-4-(5^6+7)^8))^9$
-1969101	$(1-2^*(3^4+5^6*7+8))^9$	-2252475	$(-1-2^*(3^4+(5^6+7)^8))^9$
-1970055	$(1-2^*(3^4+5^6*7-8))^9$	-2255790	$1/23^*(45-6-7^8*9)$
-1970073	$(-1-2^*(3^4+5^6*7-8))^9$	-2260647	$(1-2^*(3^4+5^6-7)^8)^9$
-1970361	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+5^6*7+8)^9$	-2260665	$(-1-2^*(3^4+5^6-7)^8)^9$
-1978803	$(1-2^*(3^4+5^6)^7-8)^9$	-2261906	$-1/(23/(4+(5^6+7^8)^9))$
-1979109	$(-1-2^*(3^4+5^6)^7+8)^9$	-2262663	$(1-2^*(3^4+5^6+7)^8)^9$
-2015467	$1/(2+3)-(4/5/6^8-7-8)^9$	-2262681	$(-1-2^*(3^4+5^6+7)^8)^9$
-2015611	$1/(2+3)-(4/5/6^8+7+8)^9$	-2290311	$(1-2/(3-4/5)^*(6^7-8))^9$
-2027619	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(-6*(7+8)-9)$	-2290329	$(-1-2/(3-4/5)^*(6^7-8))^9$
-2031181	$1+2^*(34+5^6*(7-8^9))$	-2296680	$(-1-2)^*((3+4)^*(5^6*7-8)-9)$
-2031183	$-1+2^*(34+5^6*(7-8^9))$	-2296734	$(-1-2)^*((3+4)^*(5^6*7-8)+9)$
-2031317	$1-2^*(34+5^6*(7^8+9))$	-2296824	$(-1-2)^*((3+4)^5*5^6*7-8-9)$
-2031319	$-1-2^*(34+5^6*(7^8+9))$	-2296872	$(-1-2)^*((3+4)^5*5^6*7+8-9)$
-2033655	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5/6-7^8))^9$	-2296878	$(-1-2)^*((3+4)^5*5^6*7-8+9)$
-2033673	$(-1+(2^3)^4*(5/6-7^8))^9$	-2296926	$(-1-2)^*((3+4)^5*5^6*7+8+9)$
-2049255	$(1-((2^3)^4-5^6)^7*8)^9$	-2297016	$(-1-2)^*((3+4)^*(5^6*7+8)-9)$
-2049273	$(1+((2^3)^4-5^6)^7*8)^9$	-2297070	$(-1-2)^*((3+4)^*(5^6*7+8)+9)$
-2076433	$1-(23-4)^*(5^6*7-89)$	-2314127	$(1-(2^3)^4*5)^*((6+7)^8+9)$
-2076435	$-1-(23-4)^*(5^6*7-89)$	-2314353	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6-7*(8+9))$
-2079495	$(1-((2^3)^4+5^6)^7*8)^9$	-2334606	$(1-(2^3)^4*5)^*(6^7+8^9)$
-2079513	$(1+((2^3)^4+5^6)^7*8)^9$	-2334834	$(1+(2^3)^4*5)^*(6^7-8^9)$
-2079815	$1-(23-4)^*(5^6*7+89)$	-2403000	$(1+(2-3^4*5)^67)^89$
-2079817	$-1-(23-4)^*(5^6*7+89)$	-2403178	$(-1+(2-3^4*5)^67)^89$
-2087496	$(1+(2/3^4-4-5^6)^7*(7+8))^9$	-2404204	$(1-23)^*(-4+5^6*7-89)$
-2087514	$(-1+(2/3^4-4-5^6)^7*(7+8))^9$	-2404380	$(1-23)^*(4+5^6*7-89)$
-2095095	$(1-(2^3)^4*(5/6+7^8))^9$	-2408120	$(1-23)^*(-4+5^6*7+89)$
-2095113	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5/6+7^8))^9$	-2408296	$(1-23)^*(4+5^6*7+89)$
-2098785	$(12+3)^*(4-(5^6-78)^9)$	-2424845	$1+2^*((3^4-5^6)^7*8+9)$
-2098905	$(-12-3)^*(4+(5^6-78)^9)$	-2424847	$-1+2^*((3^4-5^6)^7*8+9)$
-2107268	$1+(234-5^6*(7+8))^9$	-2424881	$1+2^*((3^4-5^6)^7*8-9)$
-2107270	$-1+(234-5^6*(7+8))^9$	-2424883	$-1+2^*((3^4-5^6)^7*8-9)$
-2111480	$1-(234+5^6*(7+8))^9$	-2425296	$(1+(23^4+5/6)^7*8)/-9$
-2111482	$-1-(234+5^6*(7+8))^9$	-2426852	$(1-(2+3^4*5)^67)^89$
-2117585	$(1-(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(7^8-9)$	-2427030	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^67)^89$
-2119845	$(12+3)^*(4-(5^6+78)^9)$	-2437319	$1+2^*(3^4-5^6*7+8+9)$
-2119965	$(-12-3)^*(4+(5^6+78)^9)$	-2437321	$-1+2^*(3^4-5^6*7+8+9)$
-2131236	$(1-(2^3)^4+5^6)^*(7+8)^9$	-2437355	$1+2^*(3^4-5^6*7+8-9)$
-2131254	$(1+(2^3)^4+5^6)^*(7+8)^9$	-2437357	$-1+2^*(3^4-5^6*7+8-9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2437414	$1 \cdot 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 + 9)$	-2543905	$-1 \cdot 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6 + 78) + 9)$
-2437415	$-1 + 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 + 9)$	-2546011	$(1 + (2^*3)^{\wedge}4) * ((5^{\wedge}6 + 7) / -8 - 9)$
-2437422	$1 + 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 78) + 9$	-2559875	$(1 - (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 * 5) * (6 + 7 * (8 + 9))$
-2437424	$-1 + 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 78) + 9$	-2560125	$(1 + (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 * 5) * (-6 - 7 * (8 + 9))$
-2437440	$1 + 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 78) - 9$	-2562339	$-1 + 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (7 - 89))$
-2437442	$-1 + 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 78) - 9$	-2562431	$1 + 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (7 - 89))$
-2437449	$1 + 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 - 9)$	-2562432	$1 * 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (7 - 89))$
-2437450	$1 * 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 - 9)$	-2562433	$-1 + 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (7 - 89))$
-2437451	$-1 + 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 - 9)$	-2562487	$-1 + 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (7 - 89))$
-2437531	$1 - 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 + 9)$	-2562567	$1 - 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * (7 - 89))$
-2437549	$1 - 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 - 9)$	-2562568	$1 * 2^*(-34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (7 - 89))$
-2437550	$1 * -2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 - 9)$	-2562569	$-1 - 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * (7 - 89))$
-2437551	$-1 - 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 - 9)$	-2562661	$1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * (7 - 89))$
-2437558	$1 - 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78) + 9$	-2564361	$(1 - 23^{\wedge}4 * 56) / (7 - 8 / 9)$
-2437560	$-1 - 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78) + 9$	-2576367	$(1 + (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 * (5 - 6 * 7)) * (8 + 9)$
-2437576	$1 - 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78) - 9$	-2576401	$(1 + (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 * (5 * 6 + 7)) * (-8 - 9)$
-2437578	$-1 - 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78) - 9$	-2622768	$(1 + 23) * (4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 + 89)$
-2437585	$1 - 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 + 9)$	-2623029	$(1 + 2) * ((3^{\wedge}4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 + 9)$
-2437586	$1 * -2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 + 9)$	-2623083	$(1 + 2) * ((3^{\wedge}4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 - 9)$
-2437643	$1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 - 9)$	-2624685	$(1 + 2) * ((3 * 4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 + 9)$
-2437645	$-1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 - 9)$	-2624730	$(1 + 2) * (3^{\wedge}4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 * 8 + 9)$
-2437679	$1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 + 9)$	-2624739	$(1 + 2) * ((3 * 4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 - 9)$
-2437681	$-1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 78 + 9)$	-2624784	$(1 + 2) * (3^{\wedge}4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 * 8 - 9)$
-2450117	$1 - 2^*((3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6) * 78 - 9)$	-2624868	$(1 + 2) * (3 + (4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 + 9)$
-2450119	$-1 - 2^*((3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6) * 78 - 9)$	-2624877	$(-1 + 2) * 3 * ((4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 + 9)$
-2450153	$1 - 2^*((3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6) * 78 + 9)$	-2624931	$(1 - 2) * 3 * ((-4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 + 9)$
-2450155	$-1 - 2^*((3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6) * 78 + 9)$	-2624940	$(1 + 2) * (-3 + (4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 - 9)$
-2456382	$(1 + 23^{\wedge}4 * (5 - 6 - 78)) / 9$	-2625060	$(1 + 2) * (3 - (4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 + 9)$
-2459097	$(1 + (2 - 3^{\wedge}4 * 5) * 678) * 9$	-2625069	$1^{\wedge}2 * 3 * ((4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 - 9)$
-2459115	$(-1 + (2 - 3^{\wedge}4 * 5) * 678) * 9$	-2625123	$1^{\wedge}2 * -3 * ((4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 + 9)$
-2468681	$1 + 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * (7 + 8 * 9))$	-2625132	$(-1 - 2) * (3 + (4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 + 9)$
-2468683	$-1 + 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * (7 + 8 * 9))$	-2625216	$(-1 - 2) * (3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 * 8 - 9)$
-2468817	$1 - 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (7 + 8 * 9))$	-2625261	$(1 + 2) * ((3 * 4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 - 9)$
-2468819	$-1 - 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (7 + 8 * 9))$	-2625270	$(-1 - 2) * (3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 * 8 + 9)$
-2483505	$(1 - (2 + 3^{\wedge}4 * 5) * 678) * 9$	-2625315	$(1 + 2) * ((3 * 4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 - 9)$
-2483523	$(1 + (2 + 3^{\wedge}4 * 5) * 678) * -9$	-2626917	$(-1 - 2) * ((3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 - 9)$
-2513485	$1 + 23^*(4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 + 89)$	-2626971	$(-1 - 2) * ((3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) * 8 + 9)$
-2513486	$1 * 23^*(4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 + 89)$	-2627040	$(1 + 23) * (4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 - 89)$
-2513487	$-1 + 23^*(4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 + 89)$	-2627232	$(-1 - 23) * (4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 + 89)$
-2513669	$1 - 23^*(4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 - 89)$	-2638581	$(-1 - 2) * ((3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6) * 7 * 8 - 9)$
-2513670	$-1 * 23^*(4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 - 89)$	-2638635	$(-1 - 2) * ((3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6) * 7 * 8 + 9)$
-2513671	$1 - 23^*(4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 - 89)$	-2641791	$(-1 + (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 * 5) * (6 - (7 + 8) * 9)$
-2514060	$1 - 23^*(4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 - 8 * 9)$	-2642049	$(1 + (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 * 5) * (6 - (7 + 8) * 9)$
-2515443	$1 + 23^*(4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) + 89$	-2667673	$(1 - 2 * 3^{\wedge}4 * (5 + 6^{\wedge}7)) / (8 + 9)$
-2515621	$1 + 23^*(4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) - 89$	-2691063	$(1 - (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 * (5 * (6 + 7) + 8)) * 9$
-2515623	$-1 + 23^*(4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) - 89$	-2691081	$(1 + (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 * (5 * (6 + 7) + 8)) * -9$
-2515629	$-1 - 23^*(4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) + 89$	-2692331	$(1 - (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 * 5 / 6) * 789$
-2515693	$1 - 23^*(4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 + 8 - 9)$	-2718587	$1 + 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2515805	$1 - 23^*(4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) - 89$	-2718589	$-1 + 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2515807	$-1 - 23^*(4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7) - 89$	-2718681	$1 + 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2516107	$1 - 23^*(4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 + 8 + 9)$	-2718682	$1 * 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2516109	$-1 - 23^*(4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 + 8 + 9)$	-2718683	$-1 + 2^*(34 - 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2517009	$(1 + ((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 - 56) * 7) * -89$	-2718725	$1 + 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2517580	$1 * 23^*(4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 - 89)$	-2718737	$-1 + 2^*(3 + 4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2517581	$-1 + 23^*(4 - 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 - 89)$	-2718747	$1 - 2^*(3 - 4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2517763	$1 - 23^*(4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 + 89)$	-2718763	$1 - 2^*(3 + 4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2517764	$-1 * 23^*(4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 + 89)$	-2718765	$-1 - 2^*(3 + 4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2517765	$-1 - 23^*(4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * 7 + 89)$	-2718817	$1 - 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2529937	$1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6 - 7) - 89)$	-2718818	$-1 * 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2529939	$-1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6 - 7) - 89)$	-2718819	$-1 - 2^*(34 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2530293	$1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6 - 7) + 89)$	-2718911	$1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2530295	$-1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6 - 7) + 89)$	-2718913	$-1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6 * (78 + 9))$
-2532205	$1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6 + 7) - 89)$	-2732575	$(1 + 2 * 3^{\wedge}4) * (5^{\wedge}6 * -7 + 8 * 9)$
-2532207	$-1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6 + 7) - 89)$	-2733950	$(1 + 2 * 3^{\wedge}4) * (5^{\wedge}6 * -7 + 8 + 9)$
-2532561	$1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6 + 7) + 89)$	-2734350	$(1 + 2 * 3^{\wedge}4) * (5^{\wedge}6 * -7 - 8 + 9)$
-2532563	$-1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6 + 7) + 89)$	-2734400	$(1 + 2 * 3^{\wedge}4) * (5^{\wedge}6 * -7 + 8 - 9)$
-2542085	$(1 - (2 * 3)^{\wedge}4) * ((5^{\wedge}6 + 7) / 8 + 9)$	-2734800	$(-1 - 2 * 3^{\wedge}4) * (5^{\wedge}6 * 7 + 8 + 9)$
-2543607	$(1 - (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 * ((5 + 6) * 7 - 8)) * 9$	-2736175	$(1 + 2 * 3^{\wedge}4) * (5^{\wedge}6 * -7 - 8 * 9)$
-2543625	$(1 + (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 * ((5 + 6) * 7 - 8)) * -9$	-2779841	$1 + 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 - (5^{\wedge}6 - 7) * 89)$
-2543867	$1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6 + 78) - 9)$	-2779843	$-1 + 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 - (5^{\wedge}6 - 7) * 89)$
-2543869	$-1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6 + 78) - 9)$	-2779979	$1 + 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 - (5^{\wedge}6 - 7) * 89)$
-2543903	$1 - 2^*(3^{\wedge}4 * (5^{\wedge}6 + 78) + 9)$	-2779991	$-1 + 2^*(3 + 4 - (5^{\wedge}6 - 7) * 89)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2780001	$1-2^*(3-4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	-3062493	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7+8-9)$
-2780017	$1-2^*(3+4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	-3062507	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7-8+9)$
-2780019	$-1-2^*(3+4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	-3062619	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9)$
-2780165	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	-3062661	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)-9)$
-2780167	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	-3062787	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)+9)$
-2782333	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	-3063004	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4/5^{\wedge}6-6*7+8*9)$
-2782335	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	-3078218	$(1-23)^*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9)$
-2782509	$1-2^*(3+4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	-3078394	$(1-23)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9)$
-2782657	$-1-2^*(3+4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	-3092355	$(1-(2+3/4)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)^*9$
-2782659	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	-3092373	$(1+(2+3/4)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)^*-9$
-2792269	$1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+89)$	-3095127	$(1-(2+3/4)^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8)^*9$
-2792271	$-1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+89)$	-3095145	$(1+(2+3/4)^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8)^*-9$
-2792627	$-1+2^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7-89)$	-3109106	$(1-23)^*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$
-2836089	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4-56)^*78)^*-9$	-3109282	$(1-23)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$
-2843541	$1-234^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)/9$	-3114573	$(1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78)/9)$
-2843543	$-1-234^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)/9$	-3123375	$(1+2^*3^*4)^*((-5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$
-2843957	$1-234^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)/9$	-3123825	$(1+2^*3^*4)^*((-5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$
-2843959	$-1-234^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)/9$	-3126175	$(1+2^*3^*4)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$
-2848923	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)/8)^*9$	-3126625	$(1+2^*3^*4)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$
-2848941	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)/8)^*9$	-3133431	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5-6*(7+8)))^*9$
-2873596	$1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$	-3133449	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*((5+6)^*7+8))^*-9$
-2874010	$1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$	-3170295	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5*6+7*8))^*9$
-2874012	$-1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$	-3182859	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*56)^*78)^*9$
-2874907	$1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7-8+9))$	-3182877	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*56)^*78)^*9$
-2874909	$-1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7-8+9))$	-3185667	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4*56)^*78)^*9$
-2875091	$1-23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-8+9))$	-3185685	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4*56)^*78)^*-9$
-2875093	$-1-23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-8+9))$	-3187152	$(-1-2)^*(3+(4*5^{\wedge}6-7)^*(8+9))$
-2876586	$1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$	-3187848	$(1+2)^*(3-(4*5^{\wedge}6+7)^*(8+9))$
-2887539	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6+(7+8)^*9)$	-3187866	$(-1-2)^*(3+(4*5^{\wedge}6+7)^*(8+9))$
-2887821	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(-6-(7+8)^*9)$	-3191259	$(1+2)^*(3+4/5)^*(-6^{\wedge}7-8+9)$
-2928575	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6))^*(7*8+9)$	-3195036	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(-67-89)$
-2928705	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6))^*(7-8*9)$	-3218136	$1+23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9)$
-2950721	$1-(23+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$	-3218137	$1*23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9)$
-2950723	$-1-(23+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$	-3218138	$-1+23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9)$
-2952897	$1^{\wedge}2*3^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)^*9)$	-3218320	$1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9)$
-2952921	$(1-2)^*3^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)^*9)$	-3218321	$-1*23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9)$
-2953329	$1^{\wedge}2*3^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)^*9)$	-3218322	$-1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9)$
-2953353	$(1-2)^*3^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)^*9)$	-3231179	$-1+23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7-8)^*9)$
-2955527	$1-(23+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$	-3231361	$1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7-8)^*9)$
-2955529	$-1-(23+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$	-3231363	$-1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7-8)^*9)$
-2978112	$12^{\wedge}3*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-78)/9)$	-3234273	$(1+2)^*(34-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$
-2991936	$-12^{\wedge}3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-78)/9)$	-3234351	$12+3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$
-2999837	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3234399	$-12-3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$
-2999839	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3234477	$(-1-2)^*(34+5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$
-2999931	$1+2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3234673	$1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7+8)^*9)$
-2999932	$1*2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3246058	$1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7*8)^*9)$
-2999933	$-1+2^*(34-5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3249904	$(1+23)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78/9)$
-2999975	$1+2^*(3*4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3250096	$(-1-23)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78/9)$
-2999987	$-1+2^*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3250428	$1+23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$
-2999997	$1-2^*(3-4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3250429	$1*23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$
-3000013	$1-2^*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3250430	$-1+23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$
-3000015	$-1-2^*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3250612	$1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$
-3000067	$1-2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3250613	$-1*23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$
-3000068	$-1*2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3250614	$-1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$
-3000069	$-1-2^*(34+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3272687	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6*7))^*(8+9)$
-3000161	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3272721	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6*7))^*(-8-9)$
-3000163	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-3281001	$(1+(2/3-4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
-3008064	$12^{\wedge}3*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+78)/9)$	-3281019	$(-1+(2/3-4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
-3021888	$-12^{\wedge}3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+78)/9)$	-3281481	$(1+(2/3-4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
-3033708	$(12+3^{\wedge}4-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7)/-89$	-3281499	$(-1+(2/3-4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
-3046632	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-8*9))$	-3306591	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*567)^*8)^*9$
-3046839	$(1+2)^*(3*4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-8*9))$	-3306599	$1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*567)^*8*9$
-3046851	$12+3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-8*9))$	-3306889	$-1-(2+3^{\wedge}4*567)^*8*9$
-3046863	$1^{\wedge}2*3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7*8+9))$	-3306897	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4*567)^*8)^*-9$
-3046887	$(1-2)^*3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7*8+9))$	-3353304	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7+89)$
-3046899	$-12-3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7*8+9))$	-3354283	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7)+89$
-3046911	$(1+2)^*(3*4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-8*9))$	-3354461	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7)-89$
-3047118	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*(7*8+9))$	-3355440	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7-89)$
-3061996	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4/5^{\wedge}6-6*7-8*9)$	-3357897	$(12+3)^*(4/5/-6^{\wedge}7-8+9)$
-3062213	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)-9)$	-3360567	$(12+3)^*(4/5/-6^{\wedge}7-89)$
-3062339	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)+9)$	-3363024	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7-89)$
-3062381	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7-8-9)$	-3364003	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7)+89$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-3364181	$-12^*(3^4*5+6^7)-89$	-3795171	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7)+8-9)$
-3365160	$-12^*(3^4*5+6^7+89)$	-3795177	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7)-8+9)$
-3373452	$(1+2)^*(3^4-(5^6-7)*8^9)$	-3795225	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7)+8+9)$
-3373476	$1^2*3^*(4-(5^6-7)*8^9)$	-3796518	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^6-7*(8+9))$
-3373500	$(-1-2)^*3^*(4+(5^6-7)*8^9)$	-3796659	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6+7-8)+9)$
-3376500	$1^2*3^*(4-(5^6+7)*8^9)$	-3796870	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^6-(7+8)/9)$
-3376524	$(-1-2)^*3^*(4+(5^6+7)*8^9)$	-3796880	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^6+(7+8)/9)$
-3376548	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4-(5^6+7)*8^9)$	-3797091	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7+8)-9)$
-3391752	$(1+23)^*(4-(5^6+78)^9)$	-3797232	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^6+7*(8+9))$
-3391944	$(-1-23)^*(4+(5^6+78)^9)$	-3798525	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6+7)-8-9)$
-3437644	$-12^*3^*(4+5^6*(7-8/9))$	-3798573	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6+7)+8-9)$
-3458893	$-12-3/45^*(6+7^8*9)$	-3798579	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6+7)-8+9)$
-3498369	$(1-2^3)^*(4*(5^6-7)*8-9)$	-3798627	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6+7)+8+9)$
-3498495	$(-1-2^3)^*(4*(5^6-7)*8+9)$	-3800493	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6+7+8)-9)$
-3499545	$(1-2^3)^*(4*5^6-7)*8-9)$	-3800547	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6+7+8)+9)$
-3500455	$(1-2^3)^*(4*5^6+7)*8+9)$	-3810456	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6+7^8)-9)$
-3501505	$(1-2^3)^*(4*(5^6+7)*8-9)$	-3810510	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6+7^8)+9)$
-3501631	$(1-2^3)^*(4*(5^6+7)*8+9)$	-3835329	$(-1-2/3^4-4*5^6)*789$
-3502071	$(1-(2^3)^4*(5+6*(7+8)))^*9$	-3843648	$(1+2)^*(34+5^6*(7-89))$
-3502089	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+6*(7+8)))^*-9$	-3843726	$12+3^*(4+5^6*(7-89))$
-3559345	$(1-(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(7+8^9)$	-3843741	$-1-2+3^*(4+5^6*(7-89))$
-3559503	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+6))^*(-7-8^9)$	-3843774	$-12-3^*(4-5^6*(7-89))$
-3593657	$1+23^*(4+5^6*(7-8-9))$	-3843852	$(1+2)^*(-34+5^6*(7-89))$
-3593659	$-1+23^*(4+5^6*(7-8-9))$	-3934295	$1-(2+34)^*(5^6*7-89)$
-3593841	$1-23^*(4-5^6*(7-8-9))$	-3934297	$-1-(2+34)^*(5^6*7-89)$
-3593843	$-1-23^*(4-5^6*(7-8-9))$	-3934440	$-12^*3^*(4+5^6*7-89)$
-3656121	$(1+2)^*(34-5^6*78+9)$	-3936576	$-12^*(3^*(4+5^6*7)-89)$
-3656175	$(1+2)^*(34-5^6*78-9)$	-3937497	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5^6*-7-8+9)$
-3656199	$12+3^*(4-5^6*78+9)$	-3937503	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^6*7-8+9)$
-3656217	$12+3^*(4-5^6*78)+9$	-3938424	$12^*(3^*(4-5^6*7)-89)$
-3656283	$-12-3^*(4+5^6*78)-9$	-3940560	$12^*3^*(4-5^6*7-89)$
-3656286	$1+2-3^*(4+5^6*78+9)$	-3940703	$1-(2+34)^*(5^6*7+89)$
-3656292	$-1-2-3^*(4+5^6*78+9)$	-3940705	$-1-(2+34)^*(5^6*7+89)$
-3656301	$-12-3^*(4+5^6*78+9)$	-3940848	$-12^*3^*(4+5^6*7+89)$
-3656325	$(-1-2)^*(34+5^6*78-9)$	-4011384	$(-1-2/(3/4/5))^*(6^7-8^9)$
-3656379	$(-1-2)^*(34+5^6*78+9)$	-4013448	$(-1-2/(3/4/5))^*(6^7+8^9)$
-3700186	$(1+23^4/5)^*(-67+8/9)$	-4018167	$(1-(2^3)^4*(5+(6+7)^8))^*9$
-3702882	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6*(7+8^9))$	-4018185	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+(6+7)^8))^*-9$
-3703089	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6*(7+8^9))$	-4078023	$(1+2)^*(34-5^6*(78+9))$
-3703101	$12+3^*(4-5^6*(7+8^9))$	-4078101	$12+3^*(4-5^6*(78+9))$
-3703113	$1^2*3^*(4-5^6*(7+8^9))$	-4078116	$-1-2+3^*(4-5^6*(78+9))$
-3703137	$(1-2)^*3^*(4+5^6*(7+8^9))$	-4078134	$1+2-3^*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
-3703149	$-12-3^*(4+5^6*(7+8^9))$	-4078139	$1^*-2-3^*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
-3703161	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4-5^6*(7+8^9))$	-4078140	$-1-2-3^*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
-3703368	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+5^6*(7+8^9))$	-4078149	$-12-3^*(4+5^6*(78+9))$
-3715721	$1+2-34^*(5^6*7-89)$	-4078227	$(-1-2)^*(34+5^6*(78+9))$
-3715722	$1^2-34^*(5^6*7-89)$	-4115115	$(1-234^*(5^6+7)/8)^*9$
-3715723	$1^2-34^*(5^6*7-89)$	-4115123	$1-234^*(5^6+7)/8^*9$
-3715725	$1-2-34^*(5^6*7-89)$	-4115125	$-1-234^*(5^6+7)/8^*9$
-3715727	$-1-2-34^*(5^6*7-89)$	-4115133	$(-1-234^*(5^6+7)/8)^*9$
-3715979	$(1+2^*(3^4-5^6*7))^*(8+9)$	-4169904	$(1+2)^*(34-(5^6-7)^*89)$
-3716299	$1+2-34^*(5^6*7-8^*9)$	-4169982	$12+3^*(4-(5^6-7)^*89)$
-3718325	$(1+2^*(3^4-5^6*7))^*(8+9)$	-4169997	$-1-2+3^*(4-(5^6-7)^*89)$
-3719141	$(1-2^*(3^4+5^6*7))^*(8+9)$	-4170015	$1+2-3^*(4+(5^6-7)^*89)$
-3719175	$(1+2^*(3^4+5^6*7))^*(-8-9)$	-4170019	$1-2-3^*(4+(5^6-7)^*89)$
-3721521	$(-1-2^*(3^4+5^6*7))^*(8+9)$	-4170020	$1^*-2-3^*(4+(5^6-7)^*89)$
-3721773	$1+2-34^*(5^6*7+89)$	-4170021	$-1-2-3^*(4+(5^6-7)^*89)$
-3721774	$1^2-34^*(5^6*7+89)$	-4170030	$-12-3^*(4+(5^6-7)^*89)$
-3721775	$1^2-34^*(5^6*7+89)$	-4170108	$(-1-2)^*(34+(5^6-7)^*89)$
-3721777	$1-2-34^*(5^6*7+89)$	-4173642	$(1+2)^*(34-(5^6+7)^*89)$
-3721778	$-1^2-34^*(5^6*7+89)$	-4173720	$12+3^*(4-(5^6+7)^*89)$
-3721779	$-1-2-34^*(5^6*7+89)$	-4173753	$1+2-3^*(4+(5^6+7)^*89)$
-3738011	$(1-2^*(3^4+5^6)^*7)^*(8+9)$	-4173768	$-12-3^*(4+(5^6+7)^*89)$
-3738045	$(-1-2^*(3^4+5^6)^*7)^*(8+9)$	-4173846	$(-1-2)^*(34+(5^6+7)^*89)$
-3778719	$12+3^4*(5-6^7+8-9)$	-4188456	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4-5)^*6^7+8^*9)$
-3778743	$-12+3^4*(5-6^7+8-9)$	-4188621	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4-5)^*6^7+8+9)$
-3779529	$12-3^4*(5+6^7+8-9)$	-4188669	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4-5)^*6^7-8+9)$
-3779553	$-12-3^4*(5+6^7+8-9)$	-4188675	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4-5)^*6^7+8-9)$
-3783294	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7^8)+9)$	-4188723	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4-5)^*6^7-8-9)$
-3793203	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7-8)-9)$	-4188888	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4-5)^*6^7-8^*9)$
-3793257	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7-8)+9)$	-4209192	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-4+5)^*6^7-8^*9)$
-3795123	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7)-8-9)$	-4209357	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-4+5)^*6^7-8-9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-4209405	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-4+5)^*6^7+8-9)$	-5140653	$(1-2^3)^*(4+5^6*(7^*8-9))$
-4209411	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-4+5)^*6^7-8+9)$	-5245692	$12*(3-4*(5^6*7-89))$
-4209459	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-4+5)^*6^7+8+9)$	-5245764	$-12*(3+4*(5^6*7-89))$
-4209624	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-4+5)^*6^7+8^*9)$	-5248650	$(-1-2/3)/(4/(5*(6^7-8)^*9))$
-4214520	$(1+2/3)^*(4^5+6^7+8)^*-9$	-5248896	$12*(3-4^*5^6*7+89)$
-4217283	$(1+2*(3^4-5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	-5249875	$12*(3-4^*5^6*7)+89$
-4217301	$(-1+2*(3^4-5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	-5250780	$12*(3-4*(5^6*7+8+9))$
-4218633	$(-1+2*(3+4-5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	-5251032	$12*(3-4^*5^6*7-89)$
-4218777	$(-1+2*(3-4-5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	-5254236	$12*(3-4*(5^6*7+89))$
-4218867	$(1-2*(3+4+5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	-5254308	$-12*(3+4*(5^6*7+89))$
-4220199	$(1-2*(3^4+5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	-5390509	$1-23*(4+5^6*(7+8)-9)$
-4220217	$(-1-2*(3^4+5^6*(7+8)))^*9$	-5390644	$1-(2+3)^*(4+5^6*(78-9))$
-4240611	$(1-2*(3^4+5^6)^*(7+8))^*9$	-5390923	$1-23*(4+5^6*(7+8)+9)$
-4240629	$(-1-2*(3^4+5^6)^*(7+8))^*9$	-5390925	$-1-23*(4+5^6*(7+8)+9)$
-4499805	$(-1-2)^*((3^4*5^6-7)^*8-9)$	-5404488	$(1+2^3-3)^*(4-5/(6/(7^8-9)))$
-4499859	$(-1-2)^*((3^4*5^6-7)^*8+9)$	-5404497	$(-1-2^3-3)^*(4+5/(6/(7^8-9)))$
-4499898	$(1+2)^*(34-5^6*(7+89))$	-5484358	$1/2*(34-5^6*78^*9)$
-4500013	$1-2-3*(4+5^6*(7+89))$	-5484392	$-1/2*(34+5^6*78^*9)$
-4500014	$1^*-2-3*(4+5^6*(7+89))$	-5539625	$(1/23-4)^*5*(6^7+89)$
-4500015	$-1-2-3*(4+5^6*(7+89))$	-5558280	$12^3-4^*(5^6-7)^*89$
-4500102	$(-1-2)^*(34+5^6*(7+89))$	-5561736	$-12^3-4^*(5^6-7)^*89$
-4500141	$(-1-2)^*((3^4*5^6+7)^*8-9)$	-5563264	$12^3-4^*(5^6+7)^*89$
-4500195	$(-1-2)^*((3^4*5^6+7)^*8+9)$	-5566720	$-12^3-4^*(5^6+7)^*89$
-4501875	$(-1-2)/(3+4)^5^(6+7-8-9)$	-5577882	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6*7^*(8+9))$
-4536393	$12-3^4/5^*(6^7+89)$	-5577930	$(1+2)^*(-3+(4-5^6*7)^*(8+9))$
-4536417	$-12-3^4/5^*(6^7+89)$	-5578089	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6*7^*(8+9))$
-4593405	$(1-(2/3+4)^*(5^6*7-8))^*9$	-5578113	$1^2*3*(4-5^6*7^*(8+9))$
-4593423	$(1+(2/3+4)^*(5^6*7-8))^*-9$	-5578137	$(1-2)^*3*(4+5^6*7^*(8+9))$
-4727673	$(-1-2*(3^4-5)^*(6^7-8))/9$	-5578161	$(1+2)^*(3^*-4-5^6*7^*(8+9))$
-4727943	$(1-2*(3^4-5)^*(6^7+8))/9$	-5578320	$(1+2)^*(3-(4+5^6*7)^*(8+9))$
-4830119	$(-1-2/3^4-4^*5^6*7)^*89$	-5578338	$(-1-2)^*(3+(4+5^6*7)^*(8+9))$
-4867364	$1/(2/(3-(4+5^6*7)^*89))$	-5578368	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+5^6*7^*(8+9))$
-4873236	$12^3-4^*(5^6*78-9)$	-5622291	$(1+(2+3)^*(4-(5^6-7)^*8))^*9$
-4873308	$12^3-4^*(5^6*78+9)$	-5622309	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4-(5^6-7)^*8))^*9$
-4874856	$12^*3*(4-5^6*78/9)$	-5622651	$(1-(2+3)^*(4+(5^6-7)^*8))^*9$
-4874928	$12^*3-4^*(5^6*78-9)$	-5622669	$(1+(2+3)^*(4+(5^6-7)^*8))^*-9$
-4874941	$1^*23-4^*(5^6*78-9)$	-5627331	$(1+(2+3)^*(4-(5^6+7)^*8))^*9$
-4874942	$-1+23-4^*(5^6*78-9)$	-5627349	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4-(5^6+7)^*8))^*9$
-4874949	$12+3-4^*(5^6*78-9)$	-5627691	$(1-(2+3)^*(4+(5^6+7)^*8))^*9$
-4874979	$-12-3-4^*(5^6*78-9)$	-5627709	$(1+(2+3)^*(4+(5^6+7)^*8))^*-9$
-4875021	$12+3-4^*(5^6*78+9)$	-5661375	$(1/23+4)^*-5^*(6^7+89)$
-4875051	$-12-3-4^*(5^6*78+9)$	-5775313	$(1-(2^3)^4*5^6)^*(7^*8-9)$
-4875058	$1-23-4^*(5^6*78+9)$	-5775407	$(1+(2^3)^4*5^6)^*(7^*-8+9)$
-4875059	$-1^*23-4^*(5^6*78+9)$	-5810607	$(1+((2^3)^4-5^6)^*7^*8)^*9$
-4875072	$-12^*3-4^*(5^6*78+9)$	-5810625	$(-1+((2^3)^4-5^6)^*7^*8)^*9$
-4875144	$-12^*3*(4+5^6*78/9)$	-5858160	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5-(6+7-8)^9)$
-4876692	$-12^3-4^*(5^6*78-9)$	-5859105	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6(-6+7+8)+9)$
-4876764	$-12^3-4^*(5^6*78+9)$	-5859150	$(1+2^*3^4)^*(5^6*7+8)+9)$
-4921326	$(1+(2+3)^*(4-5^6*7+8))^*9$	-5859159	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6(-6+7+8)-9)$
-4921506	$(1+(2-3-4)^*(5^6*7-8))^*9$	-5859591	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+5^6(-6+7+8)-9)$
-4921524	$(-1+(2-3-4)^*(5^6*7-8))^*9$	-5859600	$(1+2^*3^4)^*(5^6*7+8)-9)$
-4921704	$(1+(2+3)^*(4+5^6*7-8))^*-9$	-5859645	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+5^6(-6+7+8)+9)$
-4922046	$(1+(2+3)^*(4-5^6*7-8))^*9$	-5860590	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5+(6+7-8)^9)$
-4922226	$(1+(2-3-4)^*(5^6*7+8))^*9$	-5905593	$(1+2^*3^*(4-5^6*7+8))^*9$
-4922244	$(-1+(2-3-4)^*(5^6*7+8))^*9$	-5905611	$(-1+2^*3^*(4-5^6*7+8))^*9$
-4922406	$(1-(2+3)^*(4+5^6*7+8))^*9$	-5905881	$(1+2^*(3^*(4-5^6*7+8))^*9$
-4922424	$(1+(2+3)^*(4+5^6*7+8))^*-9$	-5905899	$(-1+2^*(3^*(4-5^6*7+8))^*9$
-4942629	$(-1-2/3^4-4^*5^6*78)^*9$	-5906025	$(1-2^*3^*(4+5^6*7-8))^*9$
-5031405	$(1+2^*(3^4*5-6^7+8))^*9$	-5906043	$(1+2^*3^*(4+5^6*7-8))^*-9$
-5031423	$(-1+2^*(3^4*5-6^7+8))^*9$	-5906169	$(1+2^*(3^*(4-5^6*7-8))^*9$
-5031693	$(1+2^*(3^4*5-6^7-8))^*9$	-5906187	$(-1+2^*(3^*(4-5^6*7-8))^*9$
-5031711	$(-1+2^*(3^4*5-6^7-8))^*9$	-5906313	$(1-2^*(3^*(4+5^6*7-8))^*9$
-5045985	$(1-2^*(3^4*5+6^7-8))^*9$	-5906331	$(1+2^*(3^*(4+5^6*7-8))^*-9$
-5046003	$(-1-2^*(3^4*5+6^7-8))^*9$	-5906457	$(1+2^*3^*(4-5^6*7-8))^*9$
-5046273	$(1-2^*(3^4*5+6^7+8))^*9$	-5906475	$(-1+2^*3^*(4-5^6*7-8))^*9$
-5046291	$(-1-2^*(3^4*5+6^7+8))^*9$	-5906601	$(1-2^*(3^*(4+5^6*7+8))^*9$
-5087628	$12^*3*(4-(5^6+78)^*9)$	-5906619	$(1+2^*(3^*(4+5^6*7+8))^*-9$
-5087916	$-12^*3*(4+(5^6+78)^*9)$	-5906889	$(1-2^*3^*(4+5^6*7+8))^*9$
-5124964	$12^*3+4^*5^6*(7-89)$	-5906907	$(1+2^*3^*(4+5^6*7+8))^*-9$
-5124985	$12+3+4^*5^6*(7-89)$	-5999985	$12+3-4^*5^6*(7+89)$
-5125015	$-12-3+4^*5^6*(7-89)$	-6000015	$-12-3-4^*5^6*(7+89)$
-5140597	$(1-2^3)^*(-4+5^6*(7^*8-9))$	-6049728	$(1-(2/3)^4-4^*5)/(6^8-7/(8/9))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-6054912	$(1+(2/3+4)^5)/(6^{\wedge}-7/(8/-9))$	-6891157	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)^*9)$
-6093749	$1-234*5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)/9$	-6949991	$-1+(2+3)^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
-6093751	$-1-234*5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)/9$	-6950029	$1-(2+3)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
-6106547	$-1+23*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*(8+9))$	-6950031	$-1-(2+3)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
-6106729	$1-23*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*(8+9))$	-6956259	$1-(2+3)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$
-6106730	$-1*23*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*(8+9))$	-7065255	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6*7*8+9)$
-6106731	$-1-23*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*(8+9))$	-7065945	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6*7*-8-9)$
-6112203	$1-23*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*(8+9))$	-7085625	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7*8))/-9$
-6124713	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*((-4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8-9)$	-7109347	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-8*9))$
-6124839	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*((-4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8+9)$	-7109403	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7*8+9))$
-6124909	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8-9)$	-7110713	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7/8))/-9$
-6124965	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8-9)$	-7312507	$-1-2*(3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78)-9)$
-6125035	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8+9)$	-7322162	$(1-2*34)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$
-6125091	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8+9)$	-7334088	$(1-2*34)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$
-6125161	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*((4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8-9)$	-7392660	$12*(-3+4/5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+89)$
-6125287	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*((4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8+9)$	-7431447	$1-2*34*(5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$
-6164022	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-7431449	$-1-2*34*(5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$
-6164059	$1/2*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-7438027	$-1-2*(34*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)-9)$
-6164062	$1/2*(-3+4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-7443551	$1-2*34*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$
-6164063	$1/2*(3-4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-7443553	$-1-2*34*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$
-6164066	$1/2*(-3-4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-7446519	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^*6*7-8))^*9$
-6164103	$-1/2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-7446537	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^*6*7-8))^*-9$
-6266871	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*(6*7-8))^*9$	-7499981	$-1+(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$
-6266889	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*(6*7-8))^*-9$	-7500019	$1-(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$
-6377188	$-12*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)-78)/9$	-7500021	$-1-(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$
-6377396	$-12*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)+78)/9$	-7540734	$(12-3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$
-6406231	$-1+(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$	-7553016	$(12-3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$
-6499964	$12*(3-4*5^{\wedge}6*78/9)$	-7603032	$12*(3+(4*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)/9)$
-6500036	$-12*(3+4*5^{\wedge}6*78/9)$	-7603104	$12*(-3+(4*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)/9)$
-6561165	$(-12-3)^*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$	-7686584	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+56+7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-6563835	$(-12-3)^*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$	-7781679	$(1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6696633	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6*7*8-9)$	-7781697	$(1-((2^*3)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*-9$
-6697287	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6*7*-8+9)$	-7858143	$(1+(234-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6708717	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$	-7858161	$(-1+(234-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6708771	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	-7865775	$(1+(2^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6716340	$-12*(3+4*(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9)$	-7865793	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6716373	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$	-7869015	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6716427	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	-7869033	$(-1+(2+3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6716613	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$	-7869303	$(1-(2-3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6716667	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	-7869321	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*-9$
-6717222	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7*8+9)$	-7871444	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8*9)$
-6717276	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7*8-9)$	-7871500	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8*9)$
-6719652	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7*8-9)$	-7872893	$1+(234-5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$
-6719706	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7*8+9)$	-7872895	$-1+(234-5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$
-6720261	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	-7873263	$(1+(2*3*4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6720315	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$	-7873281	$(-1+(2*3*4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6720501	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	-7874289	$(-1+(2*3+4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6720555	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$	-7874799	$(1+(2/(3/4)-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6728157	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$	-7874817	$(-1+(2/(3/4)-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6728211	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$	-7875183	$(1-(2/(3/4)+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6741540	$12*(3-(4*5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9)$	-7875201	$(1+(2/(3/4)+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*-9$
-6743484	$12*(3-4*(5^{\wedge}6-7-8)^*9)$	-7875711	$(1-(2*3+4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6746751	$(1+2*3*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8))^*9$	-7876719	$(1-(2*3*4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6746769	$(-1+2*3*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8))^*9$	-7876737	$(1+(2*3*4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*-9$
-6747183	$(1-2*3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8))^*9$	-7877105	$1-(234+5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$
-6747201	$(1+2*3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8))^*-9$	-7877107	$-1-(234+5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$
-6747804	$12*(3-(4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)+8)^*9)$	-7878500	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8*9)$
-6750342	$12*(3-4*(5^{\wedge}6+7/8)^*9)$	-7878556	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8*9)$
-6752799	$(1+2*3*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8))^*9$	-7880679	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6752817	$(-1+2*3*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8))^*9$	-7880697	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6753231	$(1-2*3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8))^*9$	-7880967	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6753249	$(1+2*3*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8))^*-9$	-7880985	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*-9$
-6758388	$12*(3-(4*5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$	-7884207	$(1-(2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6758460	$-12*(3+(4*5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$	-7884225	$(1+(2^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*-9$
-6783660	$12*(3-4*(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$	-7891839	$(1-(234+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-6783732	$-12*(3+4*(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9)$	-7891857	$(1+(234+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*-9$
-6796856	$-1+(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	-7896705	$(12+3^{\wedge}4/5)^*(-6^{\wedge}7-89)$
-6796894	$1-(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	-7915671	$(1+(2-(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)^*7)^*8)^*9$
-6796896	$-1-(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	-7915689	$(-1+(2-(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)^*7)^*8)^*9$
-6890093	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)^*9)$	-7915959	$(1-(2+(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)^*7)^*8)^*9$
-6890149	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)^*9)$	-7915977	$(1+(2+(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)^*7)^*8)^*-9$
-6891101	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)^*9)$	-7929480	$(1+2/3+4)^*5*(-6^{\wedge}7+8*9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-7933560	$(1+2/3+4)^* \cdot 5^*(6^{\wedge}7+8^*9)$	-9027909	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7/8-9)$
-7964775	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)/8-9)$	-9027963	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7/8+9)$
-7968303	$(1-((2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*8)^*9$	-9071010	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*(5^{\wedge}6/7-8-9)$
-7968321	$(1+((2^*3)^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*8)^*-9$	-9136530	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*(5^{\wedge}6/7+8-9)$
-7968441	$1+2-34^*(5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8)-9)$	-9144265	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*(5^{\wedge}6/7+8/9)$
-7968665	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)/-8+9)$	-9144720	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*(5^{\wedge}6/7-8+9)$
-7969053	$1+2-34^*(5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8)+9)$	-9172566	$(1-23^{\wedge}4^*5^*(67-8))/9$
-7969059	$-1-2-34^*(5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8)+9)$	-9210240	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*(5^{\wedge}6/7+8+9)$
-7978149	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7/8-9)$	-9215991	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*(6^*7+8))^*9$
-7978203	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7/8+9)$	-9216009	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*(6^*7+8))^*-9$
-7987135	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*6)^*(7^*8+9)$	-9224047	$(1-(2-3^{\wedge}-4^*5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$
-7987265	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*6)^*(7^*-8-9)$	-9224081	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}-4^*5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(-8-9)$
-8036343	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^*6^*7+8))^*9$	-9296518	$(1+(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7))^*(8+9)$
-8036361	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^*6^*7+8))^*-9$	-9296552	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7))^*(8+9)$
-8038485	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)/8+9)$	-9297198	$(1-(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7))^*(8+9)$
-8042411	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^*4))^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)/-8-9)$	-9297232	$(1+(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7))^*(-8-9)$
-8156275	$-1-2^*3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$	-9349829	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4/5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8-9)$
-8340037	$-1-2^*3^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	-9435465	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6/7+8^*9)$
-8450180	$1+(23^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6^*78)^*9$	-9504037	$(1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5-6^{\wedge}7))^*(8+9)$
-8450182	$-1+(23^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6^*78)^*9$	-9504071	$(-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5-6^{\wedge}7))^*(8+9)$
-8501814	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5-6^{\wedge}7/8)+9)$	-9531577	$(1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6^{\wedge}7))^*(8+9)$
-8501868	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5-6^{\wedge}7/8)-9)$	-9531611	$(-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6^{\wedge}7))^*(8+9)$
-8504244	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6^{\wedge}7/8)-9)$	-9623042	$(1-23)^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7-89)$
-8504298	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6^{\wedge}7/8)+9)$	-9682844	$(12+(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)^*7)^*89$
-8531175	$12-(3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*78-9)$	-9683900	$12+(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)^*7^*89$
-8531199	$-12-(3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*78-9)$	-9683924	$-12+(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)^*7^*89$
-8531301	$12-(3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*78+9)$	-9684980	$(-12+(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)^*7)^*89$
-8531325	$-12-(3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*78+9)$	-9707441	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*6)^*(7+8^*9)$
-8624907	$1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8+9))$	-9707599	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*6)^*(-7-8^*9)$
-8624909	$-1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8+9))$	-9727154	$12+(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8624967	$1+2^{\wedge}3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(78-9))$	-9727178	$-12+(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8624969	$-1+2^{\wedge}3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(78-9))$	-9731346	$1+2+(34-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8625031	$1-2^{\wedge}3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78-9))$	-9731347	$1^*2+(34-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8625033	$-1-2^{\wedge}3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78-9))$	-9731351	$1^*-2+(34-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8625091	$1-23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8+9))$	-9731352	$-1-2+(34-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8625092	$-1^*23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8+9))$	-9732291	$12^{\wedge}3+(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8625093	$-1-23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8+9))$	-9733003	$12^{\wedge}3-(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8640597	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8^*9))$	-9733983	$12^*3+(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8640653	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8^*9))$	-9734055	$12^*-3+(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8789959	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4/5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8-9)$	-9734274	$12-(3-4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8845785	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6/7-8^*9)$	-9734298	$-12-(3-4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8846847	$(1-((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*6-7)^*8)^*9$	-9734452	$12+(3-4-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8846865	$(1+((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*6-7)^*8)^*-9$	-9734476	$-12+(3-4-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8847855	$(1-((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*6+7)^*8)^*9$	-9734695	$12^*3-(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8847873	$(1+((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5^*6+7)^*8)^*-9$	-9734767	$12^*-3-(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8852154	$12-3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7-89)$	-9735747	$-12^{\wedge}3+(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8852178	$-12-3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7-89)$	-9736459	$-12^{\wedge}3-(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8866572	$12-3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+89)$	-9737398	$1+2-(34+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8866596	$-12-3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+89)$	-9737399	$1^*2-(34+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8995671	$(1+2^{\wedge}3^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8))^*9$	-9737403	$1^*-2-(34+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8995689	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8))^*9$	-9737404	$-1-2-(34+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8995905	$(1+2^*(3-4^*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8))^*9$	-9741572	$12-(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8995923	$(-1+2^*(3-4^*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8))^*9$	-9741596	$-12-(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-8996013	$(1-2^*(3+4^*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8))^*9$	-9749923	$-1+2^*(3-4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*78-9))$
-8996031	$(1+2^*(3+4^*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8))^*-9$	-9749933	$1-2^*(3+4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*78-9))$
-8996247	$(1-2^{\wedge}3^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8))^*9$	-9750067	$-1+2^*(3-4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*78+9))$
-8996265	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8))^*9$	-9750077	$1-2^*(3+4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*78+9))$
-8998929	$(1+2^*(3-(4/5^{\wedge}-6-7)^*8))^*9$	-9783770	$(12-(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)^*7)^*89$
-8998947	$(-1+2^*(3-(4/5^{\wedge}-6-7)^*8))^*9$	-9784826	$12-(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)^*7^*89$
-8999037	$(1-2^*(3+(4/5^{\wedge}-6-7)^*8))^*9$	-9784850	$-12-(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)^*7^*89$
-9000025	$-1-2^*(3+(4/5^{\wedge}-6-7)^*8))^*9$	-9785906	$(12+(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)^*7)^*-89$
-9000963	$(1+2^*(3-(4/5^{\wedge}-6+7)^*8))^*9$	-9811567	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}-4^*5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$
-9001053	$(1-2^*(3+(4/5^{\wedge}-6+7)^*8))^*9$	-9811601	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}-4^*5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(-8-9)$
-9001071	$(-1-2^*(3+(4/5^{\wedge}-6+7)^*8))^*9$	-9843021	$(1-(2^*3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7-8))^*9$
-9003735	$(1+2^{\wedge}3^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8))^*9$	-9843039	$(1+(2^*3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7-8))^*-9$
-9003753	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8))^*9$	-9844461	$(1-(2^*3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+8))^*9$
-9003969	$(1+2^*(3-4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8))^*9$	-9844479	$(1+(2^*3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+8))^*-9$
-9003987	$(-1+2^*(3-4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8))^*9$	-9945026	$(1-23^*4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7-89)$
-9004077	$(1-2^*(3+4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8))^*9$	-9961224	$(1-23^*4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+89)$
-9004095	$(1+2^*(3+4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8))^*-9$	-10054311	$1-23^*4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7-89)$
-9004311	$(1-2^{\wedge}3^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8))^*9$	-10054313	$-1-23^*4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7-89)$
-9004329	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8))^*9$	-10060452	$1-23^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7-89)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-10060453	$-1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot (4/5^{\wedge} - 6^*7 - 89)$	-10969059	$-1 \cdot 2 \cdot (34 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$
-10060454	$-1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot (4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7 - 89)$	-10969073	$1 \cdot (2 + 34 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$
-10063030	$-1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot (4^* (5^{\wedge}6^*7 + 8) - 9)$	-10969075	$-1 \cdot (2 + 34 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$
-10064548	$-1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot (4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7 + 89)$	-10969361	$1 \cdot (2^*34 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$
-10070687	$1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot 4^* (5^{\wedge}6^*7 + 89)$	-10969363	$-1 \cdot (2^*34 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$
-10070689	$-1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot 4^* (5^{\wedge}6^*7 + 89)$	-10969467	$12 \cdot (3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$
-10163598	$(-1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot 4^*) \cdot (5^{\wedge}6^*7 - 89)$	-10969491	$-12 \cdot (3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$
-10180152	$(-1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot 4^*) \cdot (5^{\wedge}6^*7 + 89)$	-10969577	$1 \cdot (23^*4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$
-10198542	$(-1 + (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^*) \cdot (6 \cdot 7^*8 \cdot 9)$	-10969579	$-1 \cdot (23^*4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$
-10199538	$(1 + (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^*) \cdot (6 \cdot 7^*8 \cdot 9)$	-10970442	$-12^{\wedge}3 + (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$
-10249967	$1 + 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 + 5^{\wedge}6^* (7 - 89))$	-10970514	$-12^{\wedge}3 - (4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$
-10249969	$-1 + 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 + 5^{\wedge}6^* (7 - 89))$	-11009544	$(1 \cdot 2^{\wedge} (3^*4 + 5) / 6) \cdot 7^*8 \cdot 9$
-10250031	$1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^* (7 - 89))$	-11010552	$(1 + 2^{\wedge} (-3 + 4^*5) / 6) \cdot 7^*8 \cdot 9$
-10250033	$-1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^* (7 - 89))$	-11025504	$(12 \cdot (3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9)$
-10318887	$(1 \cdot ((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6) \cdot 7^*8) \cdot 9$	-11025720	$(12 + (3^{\wedge}4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9) \cdot 9$
-10318905	$(1 + ((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6) \cdot 7^*8) \cdot 9$	-11119983	$1 + 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 \cdot 7) \cdot 89)$
-10324935	$(1 \cdot ((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5 + 6) \cdot 7^*8) \cdot 9$	-11119985	$-1 + 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 \cdot 7) \cdot 89)$
-10324953	$(1 + ((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5 + 6) \cdot 7^*8) \cdot 9$	-11120011	$-1 + 2^* (3 \cdot 4^* (5^{\wedge}6 \cdot 7) \cdot 89)$
-10376733	$-1 / (2 + 3) \cdot (456 + 7^{\wedge}8 \cdot 9)$	-11120047	$1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 + (5^{\wedge}6 \cdot 7) \cdot 89)$
-10444290	$(1 \cdot (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^*) \cdot (6 + 7^*8 \cdot 9)$	-11129951	$1 + 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 + 7) \cdot 89)$
-10445310	$(1 + (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^*) \cdot (6 \cdot 7^*8 \cdot 9)$	-11129953	$-1 + 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 + 7) \cdot 89)$
-10497864	$(-1 \cdot 2^3) \cdot (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*7 - 89)$	-11130015	$1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 + (5^{\wedge}6 + 7) \cdot 89)$
-10499955	$(1 + 2) \cdot ((3 \cdot 4 / 5^{\wedge} - 6^*7) \cdot 8 - 9)$	-11130017	$-1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 + (5^{\wedge}6 + 7) \cdot 89)$
-10499973	$1 \cdot 2^*3 \cdot (4 / 5^{\wedge} - 6^*7 \cdot 8 + 9)$	-11155825	$(1 + 2^*3 \cdot (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*7)) \cdot (8 + 9)$
-10500027	$1 \cdot 2^* - 3^* (4 / 5^{\wedge} - 6^*7^*8 + 9)$	-11155859	$(-1 + 2^*3 \cdot (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*7)) \cdot (8 + 9)$
-10500045	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot ((3 + 4 / 5^{\wedge} - 6^*7) \cdot 8 - 9)$	-11156641	$(1 \cdot 2^*3 \cdot (4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*7)) \cdot (8 + 9)$
-10502136	$(-1 \cdot 2^3) \cdot (4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7 + 89)$	-11156675	$(1 + 2^*3 \cdot (4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*7)) \cdot (-8 - 9)$
-10546704	$(-1 + (2 + 3) \cdot (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^* (7 + 8))) \cdot 9$	-11244951	$(1 \cdot (2^*3 + 4) \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 \cdot 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$
-10547046	$(1 \cdot (2 + 3) \cdot (4 + 5^{\wedge}6^* (7 + 8))) \cdot 9$	-11244969	$(1 + (2^*3 + 4) \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 \cdot 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$
-10761705	$(-1 \cdot 2^* (3^{\wedge} (4^*5 \cdot 6) + 7) / 8) \cdot 9$	-11250396	$12^* (3 \cdot 4^* (5^{\wedge}6^* (7 + 8) + 9))$
-10783106	$(1 + 2) \cdot ((3^*4)^{\wedge}5 \cdot 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$	-11255031	$(1 \cdot (2^*3 + 4) \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 + 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$
-10874967	$1 + 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^* (78 + 9))$	-11255049	$(1 + (2^*3 + 4) \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 + 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$
-10874969	$-1 + 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^* (78 + 9))$	-11333655	$(12 \cdot 3^{\wedge}4 \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 \cdot 78) \cdot 9)$
-10875031	$1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 + 5^{\wedge}6^* (78 + 9))$	-11333751	$12 \cdot 3^{\wedge}4 \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 \cdot 78) \cdot 9$
-10875033	$-1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 + 5^{\wedge}6^* (78 + 9))$	-11333775	$-12 \cdot 3^{\wedge}4 \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 \cdot 78) \cdot 9$
-10911735	$(1 \cdot (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot (5^*6 + 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	-11333871	$(12 + 3^{\wedge}4 \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 \cdot 78) \cdot 9) \cdot 9$
-10911753	$(1 + (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot (5^*6 + 7) \cdot 8) \cdot 9$	-11427831	$(1 \cdot (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^* (6 + 7^*8)) \cdot 9$
-10911780	$(12 + (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6) \cdot 7^*8) \cdot 9$	-11427849	$(1 + (2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^* (6 + 7^*8)) \cdot 9$
-10911996	$(-12 + (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6) \cdot 7^*8) \cdot 9$	-11447379	$(12 \cdot 3^{\wedge}4 \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 + 78) \cdot 9)$
-10966986	$12^{\wedge}3 + (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11447475	$12 \cdot 3^{\wedge}4 \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 + 78) \cdot 9$
-10967058	$12^{\wedge}3 - (4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11447499	$-12 \cdot 3^{\wedge}4 \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 + 78) \cdot 9$
-10967921	$1 + (23^*4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11447595	$(12 + 3^{\wedge}4 \cdot (5^{\wedge}6 + 78) \cdot 9) \cdot 9$
-10967923	$-1 + (23^*4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11470553	$(1 + 2) \cdot (3^{\wedge} (4 + 5) \cdot 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10968009	$12 + (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11479181	$(1 + 2) \cdot ((3 + 4)^{\wedge}5 \cdot 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10968033	$-12 + (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11494642	$-1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot (4^* (5^{\wedge}6^*7) \cdot 8 - 9)$
-10968137	$1 + (2^*34 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11520386	$(1 + 2) \cdot (3^*4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10968139	$-1 + (2^*34 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11520511	$1 + 2^* (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^6 \cdot 7^{\wedge}8 + 9)$
-10968425	$1 + (2 + 34 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11520513	$-1 + 2^* (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^6 \cdot 7^{\wedge}8 + 9)$
-10968427	$-1 + (2 + 34 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11520547	$1 + 2^* (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^6 \cdot 7^{\wedge}8 - 9)$
-10968441	$1 + 2 + (34 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11520549	$-1 + 2^* (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^6 \cdot 7^{\wedge}8 - 9)$
-10968442	$1^*2 + (34 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11526518	$12 + 3^* (4^{\wedge}5 \cdot 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10968443	$1 \cdot 2^{\wedge} + (34 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11526542	$-12 + 3^* (4^{\wedge}5 \cdot 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10968445	$1 \cdot 2 + (34 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11528387	$(1 + 2) \cdot (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10968446	$1^* - 2 + (34 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11528567	$(1 + 2) \cdot (345 \cdot 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10968447	$-1 \cdot 2 + (34 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11528594	$(-1 + 23 \cdot 4) \cdot (56 \cdot 7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10968461	$1 \cdot (2 \cdot 34 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11530610	$(1 \cdot 23 + 4) \cdot (56 + 7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10968463	$-1 \cdot (2 \cdot 34 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11530637	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot (345 + 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10968630	$12 + (3^*4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11530817	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5 + 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10968675	$12 + (3 + 4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11532662	$12 \cdot 3^* (4^{\wedge}5 + 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10968691	$1^*2^3 + (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11538655	$1 \cdot 2^* (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^6 + 7^{\wedge}8 - 9)$
-10968692	$-1 + 2^3 + (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11538657	$-1 \cdot 2^* (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^6 + 7^{\wedge}8 - 9)$
-10968808	$1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot (4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11538691	$1 \cdot 2^* (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^6 + 7^{\wedge}8 - 9)$
-10968809	$1^* - 2^3 \cdot (4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11538693	$-1 \cdot 2^* (3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5^6 + 7^{\wedge}8 + 9)$
-10968825	$-12 \cdot (3 + 4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11538818	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot (3^*4 \cdot 5 + 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10968870	$-12 \cdot (3^*4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11580023	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot ((3 + 4)^{\wedge}5 + 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10969037	$1 + (2 \cdot 34 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11588651	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot (3^{\wedge} (4 + 5) + 6^*7^{\wedge}8 / 9)$
-10969039	$-1 + (2 \cdot 34 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11615760	$(1 + (2 \cdot 3^{\wedge} (4^*5 \cdot 6))) / 7 \cdot (8 + 9)$
-10969053	$1 + 2 \cdot (34 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11615794	$(-1 + (2 \cdot 3^{\wedge} (4^*5 \cdot 6))) / 7 \cdot (8 + 9)$
-10969054	$1^*2 \cdot (34 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11813760	$12^* (3 \cdot (4 + 5^{\wedge}6^*7 + 8) \cdot 9)$
-10969055	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot (34 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11999967	$1 + 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^* (7 + 89))$
-10969057	$1 \cdot 2 \cdot (34 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-11999969	$-1 + 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 \cdot 5^{\wedge}6^* (7 + 89))$
-10969058	$1^* - 2 \cdot (34 + 5^{\wedge}6^*78) \cdot 9$	-12000031	$1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}3 \cdot (4 + 5^{\wedge}6^* (7 + 89))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-12000033	$-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$	-14625093	$-12*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*78)-9$
-12201975	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5-6*7*8))^*9$	-14625096	$12-3*4*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-12201993	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5-6*7*8))^*9$	-14625099	$12*(3/4-5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-12276098	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5+6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-14625120	$12*(3-4-5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-12329421	$-1*(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*789$	-14625135	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78)+9$
-12371175	$(1-((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4-5)*6*7*8)^*9$	-14625153	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78)-9$
-12371193	$(1+((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4-5)*6*7*8)^*-9$	-14625192	$-12*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-12401415	$(1-((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4+5)*6*7*8)^*9$	-14625252	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-12401433	$(1+((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4+5)*6*7*8)^*-9$	-14625864	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78)-9$
-12570615	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6*7*8)^*9$	-14625963	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78)+9$
-12570633	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6*7*8))^*-9$	-14625981	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78)-9$
-12656025	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)))^*9$	-14626080	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-12656043	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)))^*9$	-14700708	$-12*((3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)*78-9)$
-12656457	$(1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)))^*9$	-14700924	$-12*((3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)*78+9)$
-12656475	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)))^*-9$	-14765597	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+8))^*9$
-12744252	$12*(3-4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)*(8+9))$	-14765653	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+8))^*9$
-12769140	$-12*(3+4/5)*(6^{\wedge}7+89)$	-14874439	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7))^*(8+9)$
-12895557	$1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5+6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	-14874473	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7))^*(8+9)$
-12895559	$-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5+6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	-14874881	$(1+2*(3-4/5^{\wedge}6-7))^*(8+9)$
-12895581	$1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5-6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	-14874915	$(-1+2*(3-4/5^{\wedge}6-7))^*(8+9)$
-12895583	$-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5-6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	-14875085	$(1-2*(3+4/5^{\wedge}6-7))^*(8+9)$
-12936528	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$	-14875119	$(-1-2*(3+4/5^{\wedge}6-7))^*(8+9)$
-12937416	$12*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$	-14875527	$(1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7))^*(8+9)$
-12937584	$-12*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$	-14875561	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7))^*(8+9)$
-12938472	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$	-15111576	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-78)-9)$
-13015597	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*7*(8+9))$	-15171473	$1-(23^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*89$
-13015653	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*(8+9))$	-15171475	$-1-(23^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*89$
-13338127	$(1-2^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6^{\wedge}7)/(8+9)$	-15179628	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)-89)$
-13487318	$1-(23^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	-15181764	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)+89)$
-13487320	$-1-(23^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*78)^*9$	-15193236	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)-89)$
-13494348	$12*(3-(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)*8))^*9$	-15195372	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)+89)$
-13780233	$(1-2*(3+4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$	-15263208	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+78)-9)$
-13780251	$(1+2*(3+4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*-9$	-15263424	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+78)+9)$
-13782249	$(1-2*(3+4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$	-15374028	$12*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$
-13782267	$(1+2*(3+4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*-9$	-15374856	$12*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$
-13860855	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6*7)^*8)^*9$	-15374916	$12*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$
-13860873	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5+6*7)^*8)^*-9$	-15375084	$12*(-3-4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$
-13929857	$(1+(23^{\wedge}4*56-7)^*8)/-9$	-15375144	$12*(-3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$
-14070447	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)*(-678-9)$	-15375972	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$
-14100087	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)^*9$	-15564966	$1/(2/3-4)*(5+6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-14118663	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)^*9$	-15746796	$-12*3*(4/5^{\wedge}6-7-89)$
-14275521	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7*(8+9)))$	-15748263	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-14277951	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7*(8+9)))$	-15748281	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-14348550	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)-7*(8+9)))$	-15749361	$(1+2*(3+(4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8))^*9$
-14349264	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)+7*(8+9)))$	-15749469	$(1-2*(3-(4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8))^*9$
-14411737	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5/(6/(7^{\wedge}8-9))))$	-15749775	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8))^*9$
-14411782	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5/(6/(7^{\wedge}8+9))))$	-15749793	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8))^*9$
-14411944	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5/(6/(7^{\wedge}8-9))))$	-15749847	$(1-2*(3-4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-14412061	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4+5/(6/(7^{\wedge}8+9))))$	-15749865	$(1+2*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8))^*9$
-14412136	$1/(2/(3-45*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)))$	-15749883	$(-1+2*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8))^*9$
-14412223	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4+5/(6/(7^{\wedge}8-9))))$	-15749901	$(-1+2*(3/4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-14412268	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4+5/(6/(7^{\wedge}8+9))))$	-15749973	$(1-2*(3-4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8))^*9$
-14549076	$12*((3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)*78+9)$	-15749992	$(1-2+3)*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$
-14549292	$12*((3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)*78-9)$	-15750008	$(-1+2-3)*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8)^*9$
-14622703	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*6*7)^*(8+9)$	-15750027	$(-1+2*(3-4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8))^*9$
-14622737	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*6*7)^*(-8-9)$	-15750099	$(1-2*(3/4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-14623920	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$	-15750117	$(1-2*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8))^*9$
-14624019	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*78)+9$	-15750135	$(1+2*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8))^*-9$
-14624037	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*78)-9$	-15750153	$(-1+2*(3-4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$
-14624136	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$	-15750207	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8))^*9$
-14624748	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$	-15750225	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8))^*-9$
-14624808	$12*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$	-15750531	$(-1+2*(3-(4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8))^*9$
-14624847	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*78)+9$	-15750639	$(1+2*(3+(4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8))^*-9$
-14624865	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*78)-9$	-15751068	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4/5^{\wedge}6-7+89)$
-14624880	$12-3*4*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$	-15751737	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*-9$
-14624904	$12*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$	-15820312	$1/2-3^{\wedge}4-4/(5^{\wedge}6/(7+8)^{\wedge}9)$
-14624907	$12*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*78)+9$	-15820313	$1/-2-3^{\wedge}4-4/(5^{\wedge}6/(7+8)^{\wedge}9)$
-14624925	$12*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*78)-9$	-16116615	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$
-14624961	$12-3*(4*5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$	-16118937	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$
-14624985	$-12-3*(4*5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$	-16131063	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$
-14625039	$-12-3*(4*5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$	-16133385	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$
-14625075	$-12*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*78)+9$	-16171815	$(12+3)*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-16171935	$(-12-3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$	-17620967	$(1-2/3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8*9)$
-16282395	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*(-6-789)$	-17816389	$(-1-2/3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8*9)$
-16311528	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	-17825354	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*-7+8+9)$
-16312356	$12*(3*4-5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	-17827962	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*-7-8+9)$
-16312416	$12*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	-17828288	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*-7+8-9)$
-16312584	$-12*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	-17830896	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*-7-8-9)$
-16312644	$-12*(3*4+5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	-17839861	$(-1-2/3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8*9)$
-16313472	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$	-17999028	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$
-16588791	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*6*(7+8))^*9$	-17999916	$12*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$
-16588809	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*6*(7+8))^*-9$	-18000084	$-12*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$
-16679052	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$	-18000972	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+89))$
-16679880	$12*(3*4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$	-18281055	$(12+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-16679940	$12*(3+4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$	-18281175	$(-12-3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-16680012	$12-3*4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89$	-18281325	$(12+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-16680015	$12*(3/4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$	-18281445	$(-12-3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-16680036	$-12-3*4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89$	-18984348	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6*(6-7+8)-9)$
-16680108	$-12*(3+4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$	-18984402	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6*(6-7+8)+9)$
-16680168	$-12*(3*4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$	-19169271	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*(6+7)*8)^*9$
-16680996	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$	-19169289	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*(6+7)*8)^*-9$
-16685643	$-12-3*(4*5^{\wedge}6-7)*89$	-19218690	$(12+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$
-16689357	$12-3*(4*5^{\wedge}6+7)*89$	-19218810	$(12+3)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$
-16689381	$-12-3*(4*5^{\wedge}6+7)*89$	-19367583	$(1+((2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4-5)^6)*789$
-16694004	$12*(3^{\wedge}4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$	-19389675	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3+4+5))^6*789$
-16694832	$12*(3*4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$	-19391253	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4+5))^6*-789$
-16694892	$12*(3+4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$	-19462609	$(1+2*(34-5^{\wedge}6*7))^*89$
-16694964	$12-3*4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89$	-19462697	$1+2*(34-5^{\wedge}6*7)*89$
-16694988	$-12-3*4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89$	-19462699	$-1+2*(34-5^{\wedge}6*7)*89$
-16695060	$-12*(3+4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$	-19462787	$(-1+2*(34-5^{\wedge}6*7))^*89$
-16695120	$-12*(3*4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$	-19468587	$1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
-16695948	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$	-19468589	$-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
-16740392	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6))^*-7+8-9)$	-19468681	$1+2*(34-5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
-16753620	$12*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^6*7+89)$	-19468683	$-1+2*(34-5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
-16755756	$12*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^6*7-89)$	-19468737	$-1+2*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
-16836564	$-12*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^6*7-89)$	-19468817	$1-2*(34+5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
-16838700	$-12*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^6*7+89)$	-19468819	$-1-2*(34+5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
-16874703	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)))^*9$	-19468911	$1-2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
-16874721	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)))^*9$	-19468913	$-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
-16875279	$(1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)))^*9$	-19469457	$-1+2*(3-(4+5^{\wedge}6*7)*89)$
-16875297	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)))^*9$	-19474713	$(1-2*(34+5^{\wedge}6*7))^*89$
-16890532	$1+23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7*8-9))$	-19474801	$1-2*(34+5^{\wedge}6*7)*89$
-16890534	$-1+23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(7*8-9))$	-19474803	$-1-2*(34+5^{\wedge}6*7)*89$
-16890716	$1-23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7*8-9))$	-19474891	$(-1-2*(34+5^{\wedge}6*7))^*89$
-16890718	$-1-23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7*8-9))$	-19686051	$(1-(2+3)*4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
-17282091	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3*(456-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-19686069	$(1+(2+3)*4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*-9$
-17287086	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6-7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-19687131	$(1-(2+3)*(4/5^{\wedge}6-6*7-8))^*9$
-17287140	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6-7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-19687149	$(1+(2+3)*(4/5^{\wedge}6-6*7-8))^*-9$
-17291703	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-19687490	$(1/-2+3)*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$
-17291757	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-19687510	$(1/2-3)*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$
-17292828	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^6*7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-19687851	$(1-(2+3)*(4/5^{\wedge}6-6*7+8))^*9$
-17292882	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^6*7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-19687869	$(1+(2+3)*(4/5^{\wedge}6-6*7+8))^*-9$
-17292890	$1+(23+4)*(56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-19688931	$(1-(2+3)*4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
-17292891	$(1*23+4)*(56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-19688949	$(1+(2+3)*4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*-9$
-17292892	$-1+(23+4)*(56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-19955799	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*56*(7-8-9))$
-17293143	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6-7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-20114535	$(1-2*3^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6-7)*8-9)$
-17293233	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6-7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-20117433	$(1-2*3^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6-7)*8+9)$
-17295573	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-20124702	$-1+23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8+9)$
-17295663	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6+7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-20125530	$-1-23*((4+5^{\wedge}6*7)*8-9)$
-17295914	$1-(23+4)*(56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-20132567	$(1-2*3^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6+7)*8-9)$
-17295915	$(-1*23-4)*(56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-20135465	$(1-2*3^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6+7)*8+9)$
-17295916	$-1-(23+4)*(56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-20364405	$(-1-2*3^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6-7)*8-9)$
-17295924	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^6*7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-20367339	$(-1-2*3^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6-7)*8+9)$
-17295978	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^6*7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-20382661	$(-1-2*3^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6+7)*8-9)$
-17297049	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-20385595	$(-1-2*3^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6+7)*8+9)$
-17297103	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-20390565	$(12+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$
-17301666	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-20390685	$(-12-3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78+9))$
-17301720	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6+7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-20849970	$(12+3)^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$
-17306715	$(-1-2)^{\wedge}3*(456+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-20850090	$(-12-3)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$
-17597783	$(1-2/3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8*9)$	-20868660	$(12+3)^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$
-17606638	$(1-2*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8-9)$	-20868780	$(-12-3)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$
-17609214	$(1-2*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8-9)$	-21268360	$12-(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-89)$
-17609536	$(1-2*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8+9)$	-21268384	$-12-(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-89)$
-17612112	$(1-2*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9)$	-21275035	$12-(3^{\wedge}4-5)^6*7+89$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-21275237	$-12 - (3^4 - 5)^{*6^7 - 89}$	-22791609	$(-1 - 2^*(3^4*(5^6+7)+8))^*9$
-21281888	$12 - (3^4 - 5)^*(6^7+89)$	-22803111	$(1 - 2^*3^4*(5^6+7+8))^*9$
-21281912	$-12 - (3^4 - 5)^*(6^7+89)$	-22803129	$(-1 - 2^*3^4*(5^6+7+8))^*9$
-21874775	$(1+2^*3^4)^*(5^6*7^*-8-9)$	-22862889	$(1 - 2/3^4 - 4^*(5^6+7^*8))^*9$
-21875225	$(1+2^*3^4)^*(5^6*7^*-8-9)$	-22862907	$(-1 - 2/3^4 - 4^*(5^6+7^*8))^*9$
-21936879	$(1+2^*(34-5^6*78))^*9$	-22996560	$12^*3^*(4+(5^6-7^*8)/9)$
-21936887	$1+2^*(34-5^6*78)^*9$	-22996848	$12^*3^*(-4+(5^6-7^*8)/9)$
-21936889	$-1+2^*(34-5^6*78)^*9$	-23049484	$12^*3^*(45^6-7^*8/9)$
-21936897	$(-1+2^*(34-5^6*78))^*9$	-23051140	$12^*3^*(4^*56-7^*8/9)$
-21937337	$1+2^*(34+5^6*78)^*9$	-23057044	$12^*3^*(4+56-7^*8/9)$
-21937339	$-1+2^*(3^4-5^6*78^*9)$	-23057187	$1+(2+34)^*(56-7^*8/9)$
-21937431	$1+2^*(34-5^6*78^*9)$	-23057189	$-1+(2+34)^*(56-7^*8/9)$
-21937487	$-1+2^*(3+4-5^6*78^*9)$	-23057332	$-12^*3^*(4-56+7^*8/9)$
-21937567	$1-2^*(34+5^6*78^*9)$	-23057368	$12^*3^*(45+6-7^*8/9)$
-21937569	$-1-2^*(34+5^6*78^*9)$	-23057800	$12^*3^*(45-6-7^*8/9)$
-21937661	$1-2^*(3^4+5^6*78^*9)$	-23059378	$12^*-3^*(4+5/6+7^*8/9)$
-21937663	$-1-2^*(3^4+5^6*78^*9)$	-23060608	$-12^*3^*(45-6+7^*8/9)$
-21938103	$(1-2^*(34+5^6*78))^*9$	-23061040	$-12^*3^*(45+6+7^*8/9)$
-21938111	$1-2^*(34+5^6*78)^*9$	-23061076	$12^*3^*(4-56-7^*8/9)$
-21938113	$-1-2^*(34+5^6*78)^*9$	-23061219	$1-(2+34)^*(56+7^*8/9)$
-21938121	$(-1-2^*(34+5^6*78))^*9$	-23061221	$-1-(2+34)^*(56+7^*8/9)$
-22020192	$(1+(2^3)^4*56)^*(-7-89)$	-23061364	$-12^*3^*(4+56+7^*8/9)$
-22265625	$(1+2)^*(3+4/5)^*(-6-7+8)^9$	-23067268	$-12^*3^*(4^*56+7^*8/9)$
-22313280	$12^*(3-(4+5^6*7)^*(8+9))$	-23068924	$-12^*3^*(45^6+7^*8/9)$
-22489911	$(1-(2+3)^*4^*(5^6-7)^*8)^*9$	-23121560	$12^*3^*(4-(5^6+7^*8)/9)$
-22489929	$(1+(2+3)^*4^*(5^6-7)^*8)^*-9$	-23121848	$-12^*3^*(4+(5^6+7^*8)/9)$
-22497471	$(1-(2+3)^*(4/5^6-6-7)^*8)^*9$	-23359282	$1+23^*(4+5^6*(7-8^*9))$
-22497489	$(1+(2+3)^*(4/5^6-6-7)^*8)^*-9$	-23359284	$-1+23^*(4+5^6*(7-8^*9))$
-22499940	$(12+3)^*(4-5^6*(7+89))$	-23359466	$1-23^*(4+5^6*(7^*8+9))$
-22500060	$(-12-3)^*(4+5^6*(7+89))$	-23359468	$-1-23^*(4+5^6*(7^*8+9))$
-22502511	$(1-(2+3)^*(4/5^6-6+7)^*8)^*9$	-23623263	$(1-2^*3^*4^*(5^6*7-8))^*9$
-22502529	$(1+(2+3)^*(4/5^6-6+7)^*8)^*-9$	-23623281	$(1+2^*3^*4^*(5^6*7-8))^*-9$
-22510071	$(1-(2+3)^*4^*(5^6+7)^*8)^*9$	-23623983	$(1+(2+3^*(4-5^6*7))^*8)^*9$
-22510089	$(1+(2+3)^*4^*(5^6+7)^*8)^*-9$	-23624001	$(-1+(2+3^*(4-5^6*7))^*8)^*9$
-22642190	$-1+23^*(4-(5^6*7+8)^*9)$	-23624271	$(1-(2-3^*(4-5^6*7))^*8)^*9$
-22667190	$12+3^4*(5-6^7+89)$	-23624289	$(1+(2-3^*(4-5^6*7))^*8)^*-9$
-22667214	$-12+3^4*(5-6^7+89)$	-23624559	$(1-2^*3^*(4^*5^6*7-8))^*9$
-22668000	$12-3^4*(5+6^7-89)$	-23624577	$(-1-2^*3^*(4/5^6-6^*7-8))^*9$
-22668024	$-12-3^4*(5+6^7-89)$	-23624847	$(1-2^*(3^*4^*5^6*7-8))^*9$
-22674310	$12+3^4*(5-6^7)+89$	-23624964	$(1+2)^*(3^*4-5^6*7^*8^*9)$
-22674334	$-12+3^4*(5-6^7)+89$	-23624979	$(1+2)^*(3+4-5^6*7^*8^*9)$
-22674488	$12+3^4*(5-6^7)-89$	-23624988	$1^2*3^*(4-5^6*7^*8^*9)$
-22674512	$-12+3^4*(5-6^7)-89$	-23624997	$(1+2)^*(-3+4-5^6*7^*8^*9)$
-22675120	$12-3^4*(5+6^7)+89$	-23625003	$(1+2)^*(3-4-5^6*7^*8^*9)$
-22675144	$-12-3^4*(5+6^7)+89$	-23625012	$(1-2)^*3^*(4+5^6*7^*8^*9)$
-22675298	$12-3^4*(5+6^7)-89$	-23625021	$(-1-2)^*(3+4+5^6*7^*8^*9)$
-22675322	$-12-3^4*(5+6^7)-89$	-23625036	$(1+2)^*(3^*-4-5^6*7^*8^*9)$
-22681608	$12+3^4*(5-6^7-89)$	-23625153	$(1+2^*(3^*4^*5^6*7+8))^*-9$
-22681632	$-12+3^4*(5-6^7-89)$	-23625423	$(1-2^*3^*(4^*5^6*7+8))^*9$
-22682418	$12-3^4*(5+6^7+89)$	-23625441	$(-1-2^*3^*(4/5^6-6^*7+8))^*9$
-22682442	$-12-3^4*(5+6^7+89)$	-23625711	$(1+(2-3^*(4+5^6*7))^*8)^*9$
-22699593	$(1-2/3^4-4^*(5^6-7^*8))^*9$	-23625729	$(-1+(2-3^*(4+5^6*7))^*8)^*9$
-22699611	$(-1-2/3^4-4^*(5^6-7^*8))^*9$	-23625999	$(1-(2+3^*(4+5^6*7))^*8)^*9$
-22708215	$(1-(2^3)^4*(5+6)^*7^*8)^*9$	-23626017	$(1+(2+3^*(4+5^6*7))^*8)^*-9$
-22708233	$(1+(2^3)^4*(5+6)^*7^*8)^*-9$	-23626719	$(1-2^*3^*4^*(5^6*7+8))^*9$
-22759371	$(1-2^*3^4*(5^6-7-8))^*9$	-23626737	$(1+2^*3^*4^*(5^6*7+8))^*-9$
-22759389	$(-1-2^*3^4*(5^6-7-8))^*9$	-23677039	$(1+(2/3^4-5)^*6^7)^*(8+9)$
-22770891	$(1-2^*(3^4*(5^6-7-8))^*9$	-23677073	$(-1+(2/3^4-5)^*6^7)^*(8+9)$
-22770909	$(-1-2^*(3^4*(5^6-7-8))^*9$	-23718662	$(1-23)^*(-4+5^6*(78-9))$
-22771179	$(1-2^*(3^4*(5^6-7+8))^*9$	-23718838	$(1-23)^*(4+5^6*(78-9))$
-22771197	$(-1-2^*(3^4*(5^6-7+8))^*9$	-23912047	$(1-(2/3^4+5)^*6^7)^*(8+9)$
-22779783	$(1-2^*3^4*(5^6+7-8))^*9$	-23912081	$(1+(2/3^4+5)^*6^7)^*(-8-9)$
-22779801	$(-1-2^*3^4*(5^6+7-8))^*9$	-24066830	$12-(3^4+5)^*(6^7-89)$
-22780233	$(1-2^*(3^4/5^6-6-7^*8))^*9$	-24066854	$-12-(3^4+5)^*(6^7-89)$
-22780251	$(-1-2^*(3^4/5^6-6-7^*8))^*9$	-24074395	$12-(3^4+5)^*6^7+89$
-22782249	$(1-2^*(3^4/5^6-6+7^*8))^*9$	-24074419	$-12-(3^4+5)^*6^7+89$
-22782267	$(-1-2^*(3^4/5^6-6+7^*8))^*9$	-24074573	$12-(3^4+5)^*6^7-89$
-22782699	$(1-2^*3^4*(5^6-7+8))^*9$	-24074597	$-12-(3^4+5)^*6^7-89$
-22782717	$(-1-2^*3^4*(5^6-7+8))^*9$	-24082138	$12-(3^4+5)^*(6^7+89)$
-22791303	$(1-2^*(3^4*(5^6+7-8))^*9$	-24082162	$-12-(3^4+5)^*(6^7+89)$
-22791321	$(-1-2^*(3^4*(5^6+7-8))^*9$	-24394722	$(1+((2^3)^4-5)^*6^7)^*-89$
-22791591	$(1-2^*(3^4*(5^6+7+8))^*9$	-24424359	$(1-2^(3+4+5)^*6^7)^*89$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-24424537	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4+5)*67)^*-89$	-25593984	$-1*234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8+9)$
-24499937	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4/5^{\wedge}-6*7*8-9)$	-25593985	$-1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8+9)$
-24500063	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4/5^{\wedge}-6*7*8+9)$	-25595612	$1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)+9$
-24656087	$1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25595614	$-1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)+9$
-24656088	$1*2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25595630	$1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)-9$
-24656089	$-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25595632	$-1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)-9$
-24656225	$1+2*(3*4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25597727	$1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9)$
-24656227	$-1+2*(3*4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25597728	$-1*234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9)$
-24656235	$1+2*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25597729	$-1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9)$
-24656236	$1*2*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25610597	$1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8*9)$
-24656237	$-1+2*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25610599	$-1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8*9)$
-24656242	$(1-2+3)*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25686205	$(-1-234)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8*9)$
-24656247	$1-2*(3-4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25699130	$(-1-234)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8-9)$
-24656248	$-1*2*(3-4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25702890	$(-1-234)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8-9)$
-24656252	$1*2*(3-4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25703360	$(-1-234)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8+9)$
-24656253	$-1+2*(3-4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25707120	$(-1-234)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9)$
-24656258	$(1^{\wedge}2-3)*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25720045	$(-1-234)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8*9)$
-24656263	$1-2*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25863317	$-1+23*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)*8*9)$
-24656264	$-1*2*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25871309	$1/(2/(-34+(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^9))$
-24656265	$-1-2*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25874904	$(1+23)*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$
-24656273	$1-2*(3*4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25875096	$(-1-23)*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$
-24656275	$-1-2*(3*4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25886917	$1/2*((3+4)*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-24656411	$1-2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25933798	$1/2*(3*-4+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-24656412	$-1*2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25938534	$-1/2*(3-4^{\wedge}5*6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-24656413	$-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-25941378	$-1/2*(3-456+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-24796782	$1+23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$	-25941435	$1/2*(345-6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-24796783	$1*23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$	-25941774	$-1/2*(345-6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-24796784	$-1+23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$	-25941831	$1/2*(3-456-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-24796966	$1-23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$	-25942050	$-1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-24796967	$-1*23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$	-25949423	$-1/2*(3*4+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-24796968	$-1-23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$	-25972856	$-1/2*(3+4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-24963291	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4-5)^*678)^*-9$	-26011900	$1/(2/(34-(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^9))$
-25131879	$(1+2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+8))^*9$	-26031233	$(1-2*(3+4)/5^{\wedge}-6*7)^*(8+9)$
-25131897	$(-1+2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+8))^*9$	-26031267	$(1+(2+3*4)/5^{\wedge}-6*7)^*(-8-9)$
-25132167	$(1+2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7-8))^*9$	-26574417	$-1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-25132185	$(-1+2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7-8))^*9$	-26576154	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)-9)$
-25256295	$(1-2*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7-8))^*9$	-26576208	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)+9)$
-25256313	$(-1-2*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7-8))^*9$	-26580042	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)-9)$
-25256583	$(1-2*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7+8))^*9$	-26580096	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8)+9)$
-25256601	$(-1-2*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7+8))^*9$	-26738766	$-1/2*(3*(4+5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-25312490	$(-1+2*3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6)^*(7-8-9)$	-26812214	$(1-23)*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-25312510	$(1+2*3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6)^*(7-8-9)$	-26812390	$(1-23)*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-25312896	$12*(3-(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7+8))^*9)$	-26812610	$(1-23)*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-25467599	$(1-234)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8*9)$	-26812786	$(1-23)*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-25480414	$(1-234)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8-9)$	-26987895	$(1-2*3*4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)^*9$
-25484142	$(1-234)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8-9)$	-26987913	$(1+2*3*4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)^*-9$
-25484608	$(1-234)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8+9)$	-26996967	$(1-2*3*(4/5^{\wedge}-6-7)*8)^*9$
-25488336	$(1-234)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9)$	-26996985	$(1+2*3*(4*5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)^*-9$
-25501151	$(1-234)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8*9)$	-26998983	$(1-2*(3*4*5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)^*9$
-25508751	$12+3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7/8*9)$	-26999001	$(-1-2*(3*4/5^{\wedge}-6-7)*8)^*9$
-25508775	$-12+3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7/8*9)$	-26999487	$(1-(2*3*4/5^{\wedge}-6-7)*8)^*9$
-25509561	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7/8*9)$	-26999505	$(1+(2*3*4*5^{\wedge}6-7)*8)^*-9$
-25509585	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7/8*9)$	-27000495	$(1-(2*3*4/5^{\wedge}-6+7)*8)^*9$
-25576901	$1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8*9)$	-27000513	$(1+(2*3*4*5^{\wedge}6+7)*8)^*-9$
-25576903	$-1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8*9)$	-27000999	$(1-2*(3*4*5^{\wedge}6+7)*8)^*9$
-25589771	$1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8-9)$	-27001017	$(-1-2*(3*4/5^{\wedge}-6+7)*8)^*9$
-25589772	$-1*234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8-9)$	-27003015	$(1-2*3*(4/5^{\wedge}-6+7)*8)^*9$
-25589773	$-1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8-9)$	-27003033	$(1+2*3*(4*5^{\wedge}6+7)*8)^*-9$
-25591868	$1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)+9$	-27562486	$(1/2+3)*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$
-25591870	$-1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)+9$	-27562514	$(1/2+3)*(-4-5^{\wedge}6*7*8*9)$
-25591886	$1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)-9$	-28030950	$1+23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-25591888	$-1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8)-9$	-28030951	$1*23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-25593515	$1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8-9)$	-28030952	$-1+23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-25593516	$-1*234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8-9)$	-28031134	$1-23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-25593517	$-1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8-9)$	-28031135	$-1*23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-25593541	$1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8/9)$	-28031136	$-1-23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-25593542	$-1*234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8/9)$	-28031364	$1+23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-25593543	$-1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8/9)$	-28031365	$1*23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-25593957	$1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8/9)$	-28031366	$-1+23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-25593958	$-1*234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8/9)$	-28031548	$1-23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-25593959	$-1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8/9)$	-28031549	$-1*23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-25593983	$1-234*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8+9)$	-28031550	$-1-23*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-28038758	$-1/2^*(3+4^{\wedge}(5+6))+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-30749904	$(1+23)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89))$
-28187412	$(-1+23)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89))$	-30750096	$(1+23)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89))$
-28187588	$(1-23)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89))$	-31265532	$1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$
-28301247	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7/8-9)$	-31265533	$1^*23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$
-28315809	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7/8+9)$	-31265534	$-1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$
-28371213	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7/8-9)$	-31265716	$1-23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$
-28385811	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7/8+9)$	-31265717	$-1^*23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$
-28390532	$1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8^*9))$	-31265718	$-1-23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$
-28390534	$-1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8^*9))$	-31499415	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3-4/5^{\wedge}-6^*7)^*8)^*9$
-28390716	$1-23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8^*9))$	-31499577	$(-1+(2^*3-4/5^{\wedge}-6^*7)^*8)^*9$
-28390718	$-1-23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8^*9))$	-31499631	$(1+(2+3-4/5^{\wedge}-6^*7)^*8)^*9$
-29109855	$(1-234)^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$	-31499649	$(-1+(2+3-4/5^{\wedge}-6^*7)^*8)^*9$
-29114049	$(1-234)^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$	-31499943	$(1+(2/3-4/5^{\wedge}-6^*7)^*8)^*9$
-29135951	$(1-234)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$	-31500057	$(1+(2/3+4/5^{\wedge}-6^*7)^*8)^*9$
-29140145	$(1-234)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$	-31500351	$(1-(2+3+4/5^{\wedge}-6^*7)^*8)^*9$
-29200989	$(12+3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7))^*89$	-31500369	$(1+(2+3+4/5^{\wedge}-6^*7)^*8)^*9$
-29202045	$12+3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$	-31500423	$(1-(2^*3+4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*8)^*9$
-29202069	$-12+3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$	-31500585	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3+4/5^{\wedge}-6^*7)^*8)^*9$
-29203023	$(1+2)^*(34-5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$	-31969953	$1+23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
-29203101	$12+3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$	-31969954	$1^*23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
-29203116	$-1-2+3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$	-31969955	$-1+23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
-29203149	$-12-3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$	-31970137	$1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
-29203227	$(-1-2)^*(34+5^{\wedge}6^*7^*89)$	-31970138	$-1^*23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
-29204181	$12-3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$	-31970139	$-1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
-29204205	$-12-3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$	-31998611	$1+23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$
-29205261	$(-12-3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7))^*89$	-31998612	$1^*23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$
-29234789	$1-234^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$	-31998613	$-1+23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$
-29234790	$-1^*234^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$	-31998795	$1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$
-29234791	$-1-234^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$	-31998796	$-1^*23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$
-29239001	$1-234^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$	-31998797	$-1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$
-29239002	$-1^*234^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$	-32016384	$(1+2)^*(3^*-4)^{\wedge}5^*(6^*7+8/9)$
-29239003	$-1-234^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$	-32624904	$(1+23)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$
-29249688	$(1+23)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*78+9)$	-32625096	$(-1-23)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$
-29249880	$(-1-23)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*78-9)$	-32906034	$(12+3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*78))^*9$
-29250120	$(1+23)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*78-9)$	-32906130	$12+3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*78)^*9$
-29250312	$(-1-23)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*78+9)$	-32906148	$(1+2)^*(34-5^{\wedge}6^*78^*9)$
-29260997	$1-234^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$	-32906154	$-12+3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*78)^*9$
-29260998	$-1^*234^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$	-32906226	$12+3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*78^*9)$
-29260999	$-1-234^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$	-32906274	$-12-3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*78^*9)$
-29265209	$1-234^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$	-32906346	$12-3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*78)^*9$
-29265210	$-1^*234^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$	-32906352	$(-1-2)^*(34+5^{\wedge}6^*78^*9)$
-29265211	$-1-234^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$	-32906370	$-12-3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*78)^*9$
-29359725	$(-1-234)^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$	-32906466	$(-12-3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*78))^*9$
-29363955	$(-1-234)^*((5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$	-32999912	$(1-23)^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+89))$
-29386045	$(-1-234)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$	-33000088	$(1-23)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+89))$
-29390275	$(-1-234)^*((5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$	-33359952	$(1+23)^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
-29468657	$1+23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89))$	-33360144	$(-1-23)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$
-29468658	$1^*23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89))$	-33389856	$(1+23)^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$
-29468659	$-1+23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89))$	-33390048	$(-1-23)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$
-29468841	$1-23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89))$	-33509349	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}-4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*8+9)$
-29468842	$1^*23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89))$	-33509403	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}-4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*8-9)$
-29468843	$-1-23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89))$	-33590349	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4-5^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$
-29673216	$(-1+(2/3-4)^*5)/6^{\wedge}(-7+8-9)$	-33590403	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4-5^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$
-29906162	$(1-23)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$	-33594237	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8-9)$
-29906338	$(1-23)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9))$	-33594291	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8+9)$
-29977245	$1-234/5^*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-33675237	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}-4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*8-9)$
-29977246	$-1^*234/5^*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-33675291	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}-4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7^*8+9)$
-29977247	$-1-234/5^*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-33908418	$(-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}(6+7))/8)/9$
-30231873	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+(6/(7-8))^{\wedge}9)$	-34331808	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+89)$
-30234303	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5-(6/(7-8))^{\wedge}9)$	-34472433	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^{\wedge}6^*(78+9)$
-30235536	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))^*(5^{\wedge}6^*(7+8)+9)$	-34499907	$1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7+89))$
-30361365	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8-9)$	-34499908	$1^*23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7+89))$
-30361419	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8+9)$	-34499909	$-1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*(7+89))$
-30388581	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8-9)$	-34500091	$1-23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+89))$
-30388635	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8+9)$	-34500092	$-1^*23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+89))$
-30579956	$(1-23)^*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	-34500093	$-1-23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*(7+89))$
-30580132	$(1-23)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89)$	-34550558	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^{\wedge}6^*(7-89)$
-30607368	$(1-23)^*(-4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	-34640223	$1-(23^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-30607544	$(1-23)^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*89)$	-34640225	$-1-(23^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*89$
-30662236	$12^*(3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)/9$	-34753683	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^{\wedge}6^*(78-9)$
-30662308	$-12^*(3-4)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)/9$	-35441183	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^{\wedge}6^*((-6+78)/9)$
-30689280	$(-1-2)/((3^*4)^{\wedge}-5/(6^*7-8/9))$	-35690481	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)+(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-35691885	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)+(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9$	-40321719	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4-5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$
-35971731	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)-(5^{\wedge}6-78)^*9$	-40321737	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4-5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$
-35973135	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)-(5^{\wedge}6+78)^*9$	-40323159	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4+5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$
-35995959	$(1-2^{\wedge}3*(4/5^{\wedge}-6-7)^*8)^*9$	-40323177	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4+5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$
-35995977	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4/5^{\wedge}-6-7)^*8)^*9$	-40369095	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$
-36004023	$(1-2^{\wedge}3*(4/5^{\wedge}-6+7)^*8)^*9$	-40369113	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$
-36004041	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4/5^{\wedge}-6+7)^*8)^*9$	-40870656	$(-1-(2/3+4)^*5)/6^{\wedge}(-7+8-9)$
-36222433	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^{\wedge}((-6+78)/9)$	-40994183	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3+4+5)^*(6+7^{\wedge}8))/9$
-36350361	$12-3*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-41437191	$1+2-34*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-36350364	$(1+2)^*3-(4^*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9$	-41437192	$1^*2-34*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-36350382	$(1+2)^*(-3-(4^*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-41437193	$1^{\wedge}2-34*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-36350385	$-12-3*((4^*5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-41437195	$1-2-34*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-36909933	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9)$	-41437196	$-1^*2-34*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-36984132	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-41437197	$-1-2-34*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-36984339	$(1+2)^*(3^*4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-41437803	$1+2-34*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-36984354	$(1+2)^*(3+4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-41437804	$1^*2-34*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-36984360	$1+2+3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-41437805	$1^{\wedge}2-34*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-36984361	$1^*2+3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-41437807	$1-2-34*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-36984362	$1^{\wedge}2+3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-41437808	$-1^*2-34*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-36984363	$1^{\wedge}2^*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-41437809	$-1-2-34*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-36984364	$1-2+3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-41530515	$(1+2/3)^*(4+5+6^{\wedge}7)^*-89$
-36984365	$1^*-2+3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-41629545	$(1+2/3)^*(4+5)^{\wedge}6*(7^*-8+9)$
-36984366	$-1-2+3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-41641937	$1-234^{\wedge}(5+6-7)/8/9$
-36984372	$(-1-2)^*(3-4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-41641939	$-1-234^{\wedge}(5+6-7)/8/9$
-36984378	$(1+2)^*(3-4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-42550093	$1-2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7-89)$
-36984384	$1+2-3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-42550095	$-1-2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7-89)$
-36984385	$1^*2-3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-42550449	$1-2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+89)$
-36984386	$1^{\wedge}2-3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-42550451	$-1-2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7+89)$
-36984387	$1^{\wedge}2^*-3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-42765534	$-1+23*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7*(8+9))$
-36984388	$1-2-3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-43011955	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*(8+9)$
-36984389	$-1^*2-3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-43011989	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*(8+9)$
-36984390	$-1-2-3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-43030995	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6-7))^*(8+9)$
-36984396	$(-1-2)^*(3+4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-43031029	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6-7))^*(8+9)$
-36984411	$(-1-2)^*(3^*4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-43031471	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6+7))^*(8+9)$
-36984618	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-43031505	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6+7))^*(8+9)$
-37113058	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$	-43050511	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7))^*(8+9)$
-37191183	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^{\wedge}6*(78+9)$	-43050545	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7))^*(8+9)$
-37331808	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)-5^{\wedge}6*(7+89)$	-43235899	$1/2+(3^*4-5/6/7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-37732926	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)-9)$	-43235900	$1/-2+(3^*4-5/6/7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-37735824	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)+9)$	-43235998	$1/2-(3-4+5/6/7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-37744704	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4^*5)^*6^{\wedge}(7+8-9)$	-43235999	$1/-2-(3-4+5/6/7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-37838016	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4^*5)^*6^{\wedge}(7+8-9)$	-43236016	$1/2+(3-4-5/6/7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-38201658	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)-9)$	-43236017	$1/-2+(3-4-5/6/7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-38204592	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)+9)$	-43236115	$1/2-(3^*4+5/6/7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-38812356	$12^*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$	-43236116	$1/-2-(3^*4+5/6/7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-38812644	$-12^*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(78-9))$	-43874675	$1-(2+34)^*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-38924125	$1/2-3/4*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-43874677	$-1-(2+34)^*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-38924126	$-1/2-3/4*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-43874748	$12*(3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78)+9)$
-38937221	$12+(3-4^*5^{\wedge}6*7)^*89$	-43874820	$-12^*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-38937245	$-12+(3-4^*5^{\wedge}6*7)^*89$	-43875180	$12^*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-38937755	$12-(3+4^*5^{\wedge}6*7)^*89$	-43875252	$-12*(3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78)+9)$
-39017875	$1/2-3/4*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	-43875323	$1-(2+34)^*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-39017876	$-1/2-3/4*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	-43875325	$-1-(2+34)^*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-39373551	$(1+(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	-44471358	$-12*(3+4/56*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-39373569	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	-44932797	$(1-2^{\wedge}-3)^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-39374811	$(1+(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7^*8))^*9$	-45348643	$1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)+89)$
-39374829	$(-1+(2+3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7^*8))^*9$	-45348645	$-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)+89)$
-39375171	$(1-(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7^*8))^*9$	-45348999	$1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)-89)$
-39375189	$(1+(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7^*8))^*-9$	-45349001	$-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)-89)$
-39376431	$(1-(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*9$	-45350263	$1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)-89)$
-39376449	$(1+(2+3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7)^*8)^*-9$	-45350265	$-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)-89)$
-39481361	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*567)^*(-8-9)$	-45350619	$1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)+89)$
-40252455	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$	-45350621	$-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)+89)$
-40252473	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$	-45397814	$(1-2^{\wedge}-3)^*(4-5-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-40298391	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$	-45397821	$(1-2^{\wedge}-3)^*(-4-5-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-40298409	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$	-46117832	$12*(3+45-6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-40299831	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$	-46118984	$-12*(3+45+6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-40299849	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5-6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$	-46120028	$-12*(3^*45+6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-40303485	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7^*8))^*9$	-46124856	$12^*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$
-40303503	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7^*8))^*9$	-46124999	$1+(2+34)^*5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-40318065	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7^*8))^*9$	-46125001	$-1+(2+34)^*5^{\wedge}6*(7-89)$
-40318083	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7^*8))^*9$	-46125144	$12^*3*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*(7-89))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-46694835	$1/2*(3^4/5*(6-7^8)+9)$	-51899673	$(1+(2/(3+4))^5/6)/(7^8-8/-9)$
-46694844	$1/2*(3^4/5*(6-7^8)-9)$	-51924021	$12-(3^4*56+7^8)*9$
-47248263	$(1+2*3*(4-5^6*7)*8)*9$	-51924045	$-12-(3^4*56+7^8)*9$
-47248281	$(-1+2*3*(4-5^6*7)*8)*9$	-52023599	$1+234-(5^6+7^8)*9$
-47249775	$(1+2*3*(4-5^6*7)*8)*9$	-52023601	$-1+234-(5^6+7^8)*9$
-47249793	$(-1+2*3*(4-5^6*7)*8)*9$	-52024067	$1-234-(5^6+7^8)*9$
-47250207	$(1-2*3*(4+5^6*7)*8)*9$	-52024069	$-1-234-(5^6+7^8)*9$
-47250225	$(1+2*3*(4+5^6*7)*8)*9$	-53488446	$(1+2^{\wedge}-(3/4))*5^6*(7^8*9)$
-47251719	$(1-2*3*(4+5^6*7)*8)*9$	-53999856	$12*3*(4-5^6*(7+8))$
-47251737	$(1+2*3*(4+5^6*7)*8)*9$	-53999999	$1-(2+34)*5^6*(7+8)$
-47471599	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}-4-5)*6^{\wedge}7)*(8+9)$	-54000001	$-1-(2+34)*5^6*(7+8)$
-47471633	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}-4-5)*6^{\wedge}7)*(8+9)$	-54000144	$-12*3*(4+5^6*(7+8))$
-47706607	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}-4+5)*6^{\wedge}7)*(8+9)$	-54607278	$(1-234)*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$
-47706641	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}-4+5)*6^{\wedge}7)*(8+9)$	-54611472	$(1-234)*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$
-48148813	$1-2*((3^4+5)*6^{\wedge}7-8)$	-54841643	$1-234*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$
-48149169	$1-2*((3^4+5)*6^{\wedge}7+8)$	-54841644	$-1*234*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$
-48149171	$-1-2*((3^4+5)*6^{\wedge}7+8)$	-54841645	$-1-234*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$
-48515534	$-1-2*(3^4*5+6^{\wedge}7)*8$	-54843731	$-1+(2+3)*4-5^6*(7+8)*9$
-48671856	$-1+(2+3)*(4-5^6*7*8)$	-54845855	$1-234*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$
-48937356	$12*3*(4-5^6*(7+8))$	-54845856	$-1*234*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$
-48937644	$-12*3*(4+5^6*(7+8))$	-54845857	$-1-234*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$
-49151399	$(1-23^4*(5^6+7))/8$	-55071616	$1/2*((3^4+5)*6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-49774137	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^6*7-8))/-9$	-55076010	$(-1-234)*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$
-49827797	$1+2*(3^4*5-6^{\wedge}7*8)$	-55080240	$(-1-234)*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$
-49827799	$-1+2*(3^4*5-6^{\wedge}7*8)$	-55124847	$(1+(2-(3+4)/5^{\wedge}-6^{\wedge}7)*8)*9$
-49829417	$1-2*(3^4*5+6^{\wedge}7*8)$	-55124865	$(-1+(2-(3+4)/5^{\wedge}-6^{\wedge}7)*8)*9$
-49829419	$-1-2*(3^4*5+6^{\wedge}7*8)$	-55124972	$(1+2*3)*(4-5^6*7*8)*9$
-50039928	$12*3*(4-(5^6-7)*8)$	-55125028	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4+5^6*7*8)*9$
-50040216	$-12*3*(4+(5^6-7)*8)$	-55125135	$(1-(2+(3+4)/5^{\wedge}-6^{\wedge}7)*8)*9$
-50084784	$12*3*(4-(5^6+7)*8)$	-55125153	$(1+(2+(3+4)/5^{\wedge}-6^{\wedge}7)*8)*-9$
-50085072	$-12*3*(4+(5^6+7)*8)$	-56687076	$1/2*(3^4*5-6^{\wedge}7-8*9)$
-50246722	$(1-2^{\wedge}-(3/4))*(5^6-7^8*9)$	-57395524	$-12*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)-78/9)$
-51011037	$(1+2*3^4*(5-6^{\wedge}7/8)*9$	-57395732	$-12*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)+78/9)$
-51011055	$(-1+2*3^4*(5-6^{\wedge}7/8))*9$	-57646948	$12*(3^4-5/(6/(7^8-9)))$
-51025617	$(1-2*3^4*(5+6^{\wedge}7/8)*9$	-57647128	$12*(3^4-5/(6/(7^8+9)))$
-51025635	$(-1-2*3^4*(5+6^{\wedge}7/8))*9$	-57647335	$(12+3)*(45-6*7^8/9)$
-51742349	$1+234+(5^6-7^8)*9$	-57647767	$(1+2)*(3^4-5*6*7^8/9)$
-51742351	$-1+234+(5^6-7^8)*9$	-57647776	$12*(3^4-5/(6/(7^8-9)))$
-51742817	$1-234+(5^6-7^8)*9$	-57648253	$(-1-2)*(3^4+5*6*7^8/9)$
-51742819	$-1-234+(5^6-7^8)*9$	-57648685	$(-12-3)*(45+6*7^8/9)$
-51842373	$12+(3^4*56-7^8)*9$	-57648892	$-12*(3^4+5/(6/(7^8-9)))$
-51842397	$-12+(3^4*56-7^8)*9$	-57649072	$-12*(3^4+5/(6/(7^8+9)))$
-51880005	$12*(3+4*56)-7^8*9$	-57770739	$(1+2^{\wedge}-3)*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^8*9)$
-51880485	$12*(3+4*56)-7^8*9$	-58368609	$(1+2^{\wedge}-3)*((4-5)^{\wedge}6-7^8*9)$
-51880557	$12*(3+4*56)-7^8*9$	-58368618	$(1+2^{\wedge}-3)*(4-5-6-7^8*9)$
-51880928	$1+(2+3)*456-7^8*9$	-58368627	$(1+2^{\wedge}-3)*(4-5-6-7^8*9)$
-51880930	$-1+(2+3)*456-7^8*9$	-58499532	$12*(3-4*(5^6*78-9))$
-51881565	$12*(3^4+56)-7^8*9$	-58499604	$-12*(3+4*(5^6*78-9))$
-51881774	$1+(234+5)*6-7^8*9$	-58500396	$12*(3-4*(5^6*78+9))$
-51881776	$-1+(234+5)*6-7^8*9$	-58500468	$-12*(3+4*(5^6*78+9))$
-51881828	$1+23*(4+56)-7^8*9$	-59463550	$1/(-2+3^4)*5*(6-7^8*9)$
-51881836	$-1+(234-5)*6-7^8*9$	-60530410	$1/2-(3^4-5)/6*7^8*9$
-51882014	$-1-23*(4-56)-7^8*9$	-60530411	$1/-2-(3^4-5)/6*7^8*9$
-51882530	$1+2*(345-6)-7^8*9$	-60749976	$(1-2*3^4*5^6)*(7+8+9)$
-51882532	$-1+2*(345-6)-7^8*9$	-60750024	$(-1-2*3^4*5^6)*(7+8+9)$
-51882601	$1/2+(3^4*5/6-7^8)*9$	-61328125	$(1-2*3^4/5)*(6+7-8)^{\wedge}9$
-51882602	$-1/2+(3^4*5/6-7^8)*9$	-61509387	$-12-3*45^{\wedge}(6+7-8)/9$
-51883816	$1/2-(3^4*5/6+7^8)*9$	-61640604	$1+(2+3)*(4-5^6*78)$
-51883817	$-1/2-(3^4*5/6+7^8)*9$	-61640605	$(1+2+3)*(4-5^6*78)$
-51883886	$1-2*(345-6)-7^8*9$	-61640606	$-1+(2+3)*(4-5^6*78)$
-51883888	$-1-2*(345-6)-7^8*9$	-61640644	$1-(2+3)*(4+5^6*78)$
-51884404	$1+23*(4-56)-7^8*9$	-61640645	$(1-2*3)*(4+5^6*78)$
-51884582	$1-(234-5)*6-7^8*9$	-61640646	$-1-(2+3)*(4+5^6*78)$
-51884590	$-1-23*(4+56)-7^8*9$	-61931511	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*6*7*8)*9$
-51884642	$1-(234+5)*6-7^8*9$	-61931529	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5*6*7*8)*-9$
-51884644	$-1-(234+5)*6-7^8*9$	-62259851	$1/(2+3)*(4-5-6*7^8*9)$
-51884853	$-12*(3^4+56)-7^8*9$	-62530944	$(1+2)*(3^4*5*6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-51885488	$1-(2+3)*456-7^8*9$	-62997687	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^6*7)*8)*9$
-51885490	$-1-(2+3)*456-7^8*9$	-62997705	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^6*7)*8)*9$
-51885861	$12*(3-4*56)-7^8*9$	-62999559	$(1+2*(3-4*5^6*7)*8)*9$
-51885933	$-12*(3+4*56)-7^8*9$	-62999577	$(-1+2*(3-4*5^6*7)*8)*9$
-51886413	$12*(3-4*5*6)-7^8*9$	-62999703	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^6*7*8)*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-62999721	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-68423678	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*-7+8^*9)$
-62999955	$(-1+2*(3-4*5^{\wedge}6*7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-68458108	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*-7+8+9)$
-63000045	$(1-2*(3+4*5^{\wedge}6*7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-68468124	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*-7-8+9)$
-63000279	$(1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-68469376	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*-7+8-9)$
-63000297	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-68479392	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*-7-8-9)$
-63000423	$(1-2*(3+4*5^{\wedge}6*7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-68513822	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*-7-8*9)$
-63000441	$(1+2*(3+4*5^{\wedge}6*7^{\wedge}8))^*-9$	-69123072	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-63002295	$(1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-69123288	$12*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8-9)$
-63002313	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-69231936	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8-9)$
-63823557	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*(6^{\wedge}7-8)-9)$	-69232152	$-12*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-63823611	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*(6^{\wedge}7-8)+9)$	-69609363	$12-(3/45)^{\wedge}-6*(7-8/9)$
-63825192	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7-8*9)$	-69609387	$-12-(3/45)^{\wedge}-6*(7-8/9)$
-63825357	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7-8-9)$	-69973065	$(1+2/3)*(4+5)^{\wedge}6*(-7-8*9)$
-63825405	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7+8-9)$	-72221397	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*(6^{\wedge}7-8)-9)$
-63825411	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7+8+9)$	-72221451	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*(6^{\wedge}7-8)+9)$
-63825459	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7+8+9)$	-72223272	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*6^{\wedge}7-8*9)$
-63825624	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7+8*9)$	-72223437	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*6^{\wedge}7-8-9)$
-63827205	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*(6^{\wedge}7+8)-9)$	-72223485	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*6^{\wedge}7+8-9)$
-63827259	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*(6^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$	-72223491	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*6^{\wedge}7-8+9)$
-65234375	$(-1-2*3^{\wedge}4/5)*(6+7-8)^{\wedge}9$	-72223539	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*6^{\wedge}7+8+9)$
-66410752	$1/-2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-72223704	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*6^{\wedge}7+8*9)$
-66452614	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4/5^{\wedge}6-7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-72225525	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*(6^{\wedge}7+8)-9)$
-66475768	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)-8^{\wedge}9)$	-72225579	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*(6^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$
-66476335	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)-8^{\wedge}9)$	-73088145	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6/7*8-9)$
-66720060	$12*(3-4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$	-73124865	$(-12-3)*(4*5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-66720132	$-12*(3+4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$	-73125135	$(-12-3)*(4*5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-66742488	$12*(3-(4*5^{\wedge}6-7)*89)$	-73161855	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6/7*8+9)$
-66757440	$12*(3-(4*5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$	-73968725	$1+2*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$
-66757512	$-12*(3+(4*5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$	-73968726	$(1+2+3)*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$
-66779868	$12*(3-4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$	-73968727	$-1+2*3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$
-66779940	$-12*(3+4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)*89)$	-73968773	$1-2*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$
-67053893	$1/2*((3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-73968774	$(1+2+3)*(-4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$
-67054136	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-73968775	$-1-2*3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$
-67054217	$1/2*(-3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-76781238	$12-(3+4)*5^{\wedge}6*78*9$
-67054460	$1/2*((3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)*-7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-76781262	$-12-(3+4)*5^{\wedge}6*78*9$
-67100359	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-77759928	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
-67107268	$1/2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-77759946	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
-67108305	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4+5*(6+7)-8^{\wedge}9)$	-77771304	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
-67108415	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)+7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-77771322	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
-67108422	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)-7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-77874967	$1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
-67108542	$1/2*((3^{\wedge}4+5+6)*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-77874969	$-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
-67163268	$1/2*((3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-77875031	$1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
-67163511	$1/2*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-77875033	$-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7*89)$
-67163592	$-1/2*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-77959440	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6-7)*8-9)$
-67163835	$1/2*((3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)*-7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-77970672	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6-7)*8+9)$
-67741393	$-1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)+8^{\wedge}9)$	-78029328	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6+7)*8-9)$
-67741960	$-1/2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)+8^{\wedge}9)$	-78040560	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6+7)*8+9)$
-67931136	$(-1-2/3^{\wedge}4*5)*6^{\wedge}(7+8+9)$	-78209310	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6-7)*-8+9)$
-68021262	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$	-78220578	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6-7)*-8-9)$
-68021316	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7+8)-9)$	-78279422	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6+7)*-8+9)$
-68023182	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)+8+9)$	-78290690	$(1+(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*((5^{\wedge}6+7)*-8-9)$
-68023230	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)-8+9)$	-79554263	$(-1-2/3*4/5)*(6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-68023236	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)+8-9)$	-80985159	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4/5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-68023284	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)-8-9)$	-80985177	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4/5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-68023692	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7-8)-9)$	-81655647	$(1-2*34)*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-68023746	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7-8)+9)$	-81656853	$(1-2*34)*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-68025150	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7-8)+9)$	-81697140	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*9$
-68025204	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7-8)-9)$	-81697158	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8))^*-9$
-68025612	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)-8-9)$	-81709092	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*9$
-68025660	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)+8-9)$	-81709110	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8))^*-9$
-68025666	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)-8+9)$	-82874387	$1-2*34*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-68025714	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)+8+9)$	-82874389	$-1-2*34*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-68027580	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7+8)-9)$	-82875611	$1-2*34*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-68027634	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$	-82875613	$-1-2*34*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-68139557	$(12-(3+4)*5^{\wedge}6*7)*89$	-83236920	$(1+2)*((3-4*5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-68141693	$(12+(3+4)*5^{\wedge}6*7)*-89$	-84093129	$(12-3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-68205072	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8*9)$	-84094371	$(12-3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-68239392	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8-9)$	-84817537	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*((4*5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-68249376	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8-9)$	-86092425	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)-7*8))^*9$
-68250624	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7-8+9)$	-86092443	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)-7*8))^*9$
-68260608	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8+9)$	-86093163	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)-7-8))^*9$
-68294928	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6*7+8*9)$	-86093181	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)-7-8))^*9$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-86093415	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)+7-8))^*9$	-101249973	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7/8-9)$
-86093469	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)-7+8))^*9$	-101250027	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}-4*(5*6)^{\wedge}7/8+9)$
-86093703	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)+7+8))^*9$	-103485099	$1+2*(34+(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-86093721	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)+7+8))^*9$	-103485237	$-1-2*(34-(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-86094441	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)+7*8))^*9$	-103735099	$1+2*(34+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-86094459	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)+7*8))^*9$	-103735101	$-1+2*(34+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-86296847	$(1+2*3)*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-103735235	$1-2*(34-5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-86296903	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-103735237	$-1-2*(34-5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-86470548	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5/6/7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-103750371	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-86470566	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4-5/6/7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-103750389	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-86471193	$12+3*45*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-103757121	$(1+2*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-86471217	$-12+3*45*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-103757139	$(-1+2*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-86472813	$12-3*45*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-103757345	$1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*56-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-86472837	$-12-3*45*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-103757347	$-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*56-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-86473464	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4+5/6/7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-103758201	$(1+2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-86473482	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+5/6/7^{\wedge}8))^*-9$	-103758219	$(-1+2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-87749967	$1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78*9)$	-103759011	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-87749969	$-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*78*9)$	-103759029	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-87750031	$1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78*9)$	-103759227	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-87750033	$-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*78*9)$	-103759245	$(-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-87890454	$(-1+(2+3)*(4-5^{\wedge}(-6+7+8)))^*9$	-103762277	$1+2*(345*6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-87890796	$(-1+(2+3)*(4+5^{\wedge}(-6+7+8)))^*9$	-103762279	$-1+2*(345*6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-88835175	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)^*9$	-103765176	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6*7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-88835193	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*8)^*9$	-103765365	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6*(7^{\wedge}8+9))$
-88914807	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8)^*9$	-103765669	$1+2*(34*(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-88914825	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4)*(5^{\wedge}6+7)^*8)^*9$	-103765841	$1+2*((3+45)^*6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-88942548	$12/(3+4)*(56-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-103765883	$1-2*(3-45*6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-88942740	$-12/(3+4)*(56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-103765949	$1+2*((34+5)^*6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-91084023	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*8)^*9$	-103766089	$1+2*(34*5-6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-91084041	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*8)^*9$	-103766145	$-1+2*(3^{\wedge}4+56-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-91084311	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*8)^*9$	-103766691	$1-2*(3^{\wedge}4+56+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-91084329	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*8)^*-9$	-103767471	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6*(7^{\wedge}8-9))$
-91165671	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7))^*8)^*9$	-103767660	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6*7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-91165689	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7))^*8)^*9$	-103770557	$1-2*(345*6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-91165959	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7))^*8)^*9$	-103770559	$-1-2*(345*6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-91165977	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7))^*8)^*-9$	-103773591	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6+7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-92228752	$12*3*4*(56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-103773609	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6+7^{\wedge}8))^*-9$
-92235736	$(1+23)*(45-6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-103773807	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6+7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-92237896	$(-1-23)*(45+6*7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-103773825	$(1+2*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6+7^{\wedge}8))^*-9$
-92244880	$-12*3*4*(56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-103774617	$(1-2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-93333159	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*8)^*9$	-103774635	$(-1-2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-93333177	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*8)^*-9$	-103775489	$1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*56+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-93416823	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7))^*8)^*9$	-103775491	$-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*56+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-93416841	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7))^*8)^*-9$	-103775697	$(1-2*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-94499847	$(1+(2-3*4/(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*8)^*9$	-103775715	$(-1-2*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-94499865	$(-1+(2-3*4/(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*8)^*9$	-103782447	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-94500135	$(1-(2+3*4/(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*8)^*9$	-103782465	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8))^*9$
-94500153	$(1+(2+3*4/(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*8)^*-9$	-103797599	$1+2*(34-5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-95119216	$1/2+(3-4-5/6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$	-103797601	$-1+2*(34-5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-95119217	$-1/2+(3-4-5/6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$	-103797735	$1-2*(34+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-97361185	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4-5)*(6+7^{\wedge}8))/9$	-103797737	$-1-2*(34+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$
-98624967	$1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-104047599	$1+2*(34-(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-98624968	$1*2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-104047600	$1*2*(34-(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-98624969	$-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-104047736	$-1*2*(34+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-98625031	$1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-104047737	$-1-2*(34+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-98625032	$-1*2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-105402465	$(1+2/3)/((4+5)^{\wedge}-6/-7/(8+9))$
-98625033	$-1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-106225992	$-12*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7-89)$
-98718009	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$	-106399008	$-12*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*7+89)$
-98718033	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$	-106968974	$(-1+(2*3^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8))/9$
-98719467	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$	-109979871	$(12-3^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-89)$
-98719491	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$	-110049825	$(12-3^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+89)$
-98825160	$(1+2/3)/((4-5-6)^{\wedge}-7/8/9)$	-110905431	$(1-23*4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-100086528	$(-1-2)/(3^{\wedge}4-5)^{\wedge}(6+7-8-9)$	-110907069	$(1-23*4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-100527975	$(1+(2+(3^{\wedge}-4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$	-112124171	$1-23*4*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-100527993	$(-1+(2+(3^{\wedge}-4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$	-112124173	$-1-23*4*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-100528263	$(1-(2-(3^{\wedge}-4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$	-112125827	$1-23*4*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-100528281	$(1+(2-(3^{\wedge}-4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*-9$	-112125829	$-1-23*4*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-100563646	$(1+(2*3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8))/9$	-112589094	$(12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*89$
-101025639	$(1+(2-(3^{\wedge}-4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$	-112590150	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89$
-101025657	$(-1+(2-(3^{\wedge}-4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$	-112590174	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89$
-101025927	$(1-(2+(3^{\wedge}-4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$	-112591230	$(12+3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*-89$
-101025945	$(1+(2+(3^{\wedge}-4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*-9$	-112690020	$(12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7))^*89$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-112691076	$12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7) \cdot 89$	-131625468	$-12 \cdot (3 + (4 + 5^6 \cdot 78) \cdot 9)$
-112691100	$-12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7) \cdot 89$	-131625756	$-12 \cdot (3 + 4 + 5^6 \cdot 78) \cdot 9$
-112692156	$(12 + 3^4 \cdot (5^6 + 7)) \cdot -89$	-131633748	$-12 \cdot (3^4 + 5^6 \cdot 78) \cdot 9$
-112873839	$(-1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}(3+4)) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 - 9)$	-132591664	$1 - 23 \cdot (4+5) \cdot (6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-112876161	$(-1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}(3+4)) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 + 9)$	-132677632	$(-1 + (2^{\wedge} - 3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot (5 + 6 \cdot 7)) \cdot 8^{\wedge}9$
-113338023	$12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot (6^{\wedge}7 - 89)$	-133005312	$(-1 + (2^{\wedge} - 3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot (5 \cdot 6 + 7)) \cdot 8^{\wedge}9$
-113338047	$-12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot (6^{\wedge}7 - 89)$	-134163212	$12 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 + 6 + 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-113342913	$(-1 \cdot 23 \cdot 4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 78 - 9)$	-134163380	$12 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 + 6 - 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-113344587	$(-1 \cdot 23 \cdot 4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 78 + 9)$	-134211884	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6 + 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-113366859	$12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 \cdot 6^{\wedge}7 - 89)$	-134212064	$12 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 + 6 + 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-113366883	$-12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 \cdot 6^{\wedge}7 - 89)$	-134212694	$12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 - 6 - 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-113381277	$12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 \cdot 6^{\wedge}7 + 89)$	-134212718	$-12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 - 6 - 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-113381301	$-12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 \cdot 6^{\wedge}7 + 89)$	-134213672	$12 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 - 6 - 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-113410113	$12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot (6^{\wedge}7 + 89)$	-134221784	$-12 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 - 6 - 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-113410137	$-12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 5 \cdot (6^{\wedge}7 + 89)$	-134222738	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5 - 6 - 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-114791061	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot ((3^{\wedge}(4 \cdot 5 - 6) - 7) \cdot 8 - 9)$	-134222762	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5 - 6 - 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-114791115	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot ((3^{\wedge}(4 \cdot 5 - 6) - 7) \cdot 8 + 9)$	-134223392	$-12 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 + 6 + 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-114791397	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot ((3^{\wedge}(4 \cdot 5 - 6) + 7) \cdot 8 - 9)$	-134223572	$-12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6 + 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-114791451	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot ((3^{\wedge}(4 \cdot 5 - 6) + 7) \cdot 8 + 9)$	-134272076	$-12 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 - 6 - 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-115638272	$(-1 + (2^{\wedge} - 3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot 567) \cdot 8^{\wedge}9$	-134272244	$-12 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 + 6 + 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-116696199	$(12 + 3^4 \cdot 5) \cdot (-6^{\wedge}7 + 89)$	-135757824	$(1 + (2^{\wedge} - 3)^{\wedge}4 \cdot (5 + 6 \cdot 7)) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-116770425	$(12 + 3^4 \cdot 5) \cdot (-6^{\wedge}7 - 89)$	-136048479	$12 + 3^4 \cdot (5 - 6 - 7) \cdot -8^{\wedge}9$
-116808192	$12 \cdot (3 + (4 - 5^6 \cdot 7) \cdot 89)$	-136048503	$-12 + 3^4 \cdot (5 - 6^{\wedge}(7 - 8 + 9))$
-116808264	$12 \cdot (-3 + (4 - 5^6 \cdot 7) \cdot 89)$	-136049289	$12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6^{\wedge}(7 - 8 + 9))$
-116812416	$12 \cdot (3 + 4 - 5^6 \cdot 7 \cdot 89)$	-136049313	$-12 \cdot 3^4 \cdot (5 + 6^{\wedge}(7 - 8 + 9))$
-116812584	$-12 \cdot (3 + 4 + 5^6 \cdot 7 \cdot 89)$	-136687381	$-12 / (3/45)^{\wedge}6 + 7 \cdot (8 + 9)$
-116813568	$12 \cdot (3 - 4 - 5^6 \cdot 7) \cdot 89$	-136687499	$-12 / (3/45)^{\wedge}6 - (7 - 8)^{\wedge}9$
-116816736	$12 \cdot (3 - (4 + 5^6 \cdot 7) \cdot 89)$	-136687501	$-12 / (3/45)^{\wedge}6 + (7 - 8)^{\wedge}9$
-116816808	$-12 \cdot (3 + (4 + 5^6 \cdot 7) \cdot 89)$	-136687619	$-12 / (3/45)^{\wedge}6 - 7 \cdot (8 + 9)$
-117647639	$(1 - 2/3^{\wedge}4 \cdot 5) \cdot (6 - 7 - 8^{\wedge}9)$	-138353604	$12 \cdot 3 \cdot (45 - 6 \cdot 7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-117900891	$(1 + 2) \cdot (3 \cdot 4^{\wedge}(5 + 6) - 7^{\wedge}8 \cdot 9)$	-140873551	$(1 - 2/3^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 - 9)$
-121059606	$(1 + 2) \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 - (6 - 7 + 8)^{\wedge}9)$	-140876449	$(1 - 2/3^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 + 9)$
-121062036	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 + (6 - 7 + 8)^{\wedge}9)$	-141547385	$(1 - (2 \cdot 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 - 9)$
-123795904	$1/2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5 - 5 \cdot 6^{\wedge}7 - 8^{\wedge}9)$	-141618610	$(1 - (2 \cdot 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 - 8 - 9)$
-124061949	$(1 - (2 - 3/4)^{\wedge}5) \cdot 6^{\wedge}(- 7 + 8 + 9)$	-141639330	$(1 - (2 \cdot 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 8 - 9)$
-124262868	$(12 + (3^{\wedge}4 - 4 - 5) \cdot 6^{\wedge}7) \cdot 89$	-141641920	$(1 - (2 \cdot 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 - 8 + 9)$
-124263924	$12 + (3^{\wedge}4 - 4 - 5) \cdot 6^{\wedge}7 \cdot 89$	-141662640	$(1 - (2 \cdot 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 8 + 9)$
-124263948	$-12 + (3^{\wedge}4 - 4 - 5) \cdot 6^{\wedge}7 \cdot 89$	-141733865	$(1 - (2 \cdot 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 8 \cdot 9)$
-124265004	$(-12 + (3^{\wedge}4 - 4 - 5) \cdot 6^{\wedge}7) \cdot 89$	-141765991	$(1 + (2 \cdot 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (-5^6 \cdot 7 + 8 \cdot 9)$
-124564299	$12 + (3^{\wedge}4 - 5 \cdot 6^{\wedge}7) \cdot 89$	-141837326	$(1 + (2 \cdot 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 8 + 9)$
-124564323	$-12 + (3^{\wedge}4 - 5 \cdot 6^{\wedge}7) \cdot 89$	-141858078	$(1 + (2 \cdot 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 - 8 + 9)$
-124578717	$12 - (3^{\wedge}4 + 5 \cdot 6^{\wedge}7) \cdot 89$	-141860672	$(1 + (2 \cdot 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 - 8 - 9)$
-124578741	$-12 - (3^{\wedge}4 + 5 \cdot 6^{\wedge}7) \cdot 89$	-141881424	$(1 + (2 \cdot 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 - 8 - 9)$
-124878036	$(12 - (3^{\wedge}4 - 4 + 5) \cdot 6^{\wedge}7) \cdot 89$	-141952759	$(1 + (2 \cdot 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (-5^6 \cdot 7 - 8 \cdot 9)$
-124879092	$12 - (3^{\wedge}4 - 4 + 5) \cdot 6^{\wedge}7 \cdot 89$	-142623533	$(-1 - 2/3^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 - 9)$
-124879116	$-12 - (3^{\wedge}4 - 4 + 5) \cdot 6^{\wedge}7 \cdot 89$	-142626467	$(-1 - 2/3^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8 + 9)$
-124880172	$(12 + (3^{\wedge}4 - 4 + 5) \cdot 6^{\wedge}7) \cdot -89$	-143066703	$12 + 3 \cdot (4^{\wedge}(5 + 6) - 7^{\wedge}8 \cdot 9)$
-125990775	$(1 - 2^{\wedge}(3+4)) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 - 8) \cdot 9$	-143066706	$(1 + 2) \cdot (3 + 4^{\wedge}(5 + 6) - 7^{\wedge}8 \cdot 9)$
-125990793	$(-1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}(3+4)) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 - 8) \cdot 9$	-143066724	$(-1 \cdot 2) \cdot (3 - 4^{\wedge}(5 + 6) + 7^{\wedge}8 \cdot 9)$
-126009207	$(1 - 2^{\wedge}(3+4)) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 8) \cdot 9$	-143066727	$-12 + 3 \cdot (4^{\wedge}(5 + 6) - 7^{\wedge}8 \cdot 9)$
-126009225	$(-1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}(3+4)) \cdot (5^6 \cdot 7 + 8) \cdot 9$	-143935479	$(1 - 2^{\wedge}(3+4)) \cdot (5^6 - 7) \cdot 8 \cdot 9$
-126547659	$(1 - 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5^6 + 7^{\wedge}8)) \cdot 9$	-143935497	$(-1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}(3+4)) \cdot (5^6 - 7) \cdot 8 \cdot 9$
-126547677	$(-1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3^4 \cdot 5^6 + 7^{\wedge}8)) \cdot 9$	-144064503	$(1 - 2^{\wedge}(3+4)) \cdot (5^6 + 7) \cdot 8 \cdot 9$
-127398343	$(1 - 2^{\wedge}(3+4+5)) \cdot (6^{\wedge}7 - 8) \cdot 9$	-144064521	$(-1 \cdot 2^{\wedge}(3+4)) \cdot (5^6 + 7) \cdot 8 \cdot 9$
-127405625	$(1 + 2^{\wedge}(3+4+5)) \cdot (6^{\wedge}7 + 8) \cdot 9$	-144119788	$12 - (3^{\wedge}4 - 56) \cdot (7^{\wedge}8 - 9)$
-127859096	$(1 - 2 \cdot (3^{\wedge}(4 \cdot 5) / 6 - 7^{\wedge}8)) / 9$	-144119812	$-12 - (3^{\wedge}4 - 56) \cdot (7^{\wedge}8 - 9)$
-129707914	$1/2 + 3 \cdot (4 - 5/6/7^{\wedge}8 - 8) \cdot 9$	-144120238	$12 - (3^{\wedge}4 - 56) \cdot (7^{\wedge}8 + 9)$
-129707915	$1/2 + 3 \cdot (4 - 5/6/7^{\wedge}8 - 8) \cdot 9$	-144120262	$-12 - (3^{\wedge}4 - 56) \cdot (7^{\wedge}8 + 9)$
-129708021	$1/2 \cdot (3 - (4 - 5 + 6) \cdot 7^{\wedge}8 \cdot 9)$	-145272825	$(1 + (2 + 3 \cdot 4) / (5 / (6 - 7^{\wedge}8))) \cdot 9$
-129708048	$1/2 \cdot (-3^{\wedge}4 + 5 \cdot (6 - 7^{\wedge}8 \cdot 9))$	-145272843	$(-1 + (2 + 3 \cdot 4) / (5 / (6 - 7^{\wedge}8))) \cdot 9$
-129708078	$-1/2 \cdot (3^{\wedge}4 + 5 \cdot (6 + 7^{\wedge}8 \cdot 9))$	-146015565	$(12 + 3) \cdot (4 - 5^6 \cdot 7 \cdot 89)$
-129708130	$1/2 - 3 \cdot (4 + 5/6/7^{\wedge}8 - 8) \cdot 9$	-146015685	$(-12 - 3) \cdot (4 + 5^6 \cdot 7 \cdot 89)$
-129708131	$1/2 - 3 \cdot (4 + 5/6/7^{\wedge}8 - 8) \cdot 9$	-146228575	$1 + 234 \cdot (5^6 - 7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-130421230	$(-1 \cdot 2 \cdot (3^{\wedge}(4 \cdot 5) / 6 + 7^{\wedge}8)) / 9$	-146228576	$1 \cdot 234 \cdot (5^6 - 7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-130691211	$12 + (3 - 45)^{\wedge}(6 + 7 - 8) + 9$	-146228577	$-1 + 234 \cdot (5^6 - 7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-131616252	$12 \cdot (3^{\wedge}4 - 5^6 \cdot 78) \cdot 9$	-146244384	$(1 - (2 + 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot (7 + 8) - 9)$
-131624244	$12 \cdot (3 + 4 - 5^6 \cdot 78) \cdot 9$	-146255616	$(1 - (2 + 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot (7 + 8) + 9)$
-131624532	$12 \cdot (3 + (4 - 5^6 \cdot 78) \cdot 9)$	-146691675	$(1 + 2) \cdot ((3 + 4 + 5)^{\wedge}6 - 7^{\wedge}8 \cdot 9)$
-131624604	$12 \cdot (-3 + (4 - 5^6 \cdot 78) \cdot 9)$	-146713116	$(1 + (2 + 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot (-7 - 8) + 9)$
-131624916	$12 \cdot (3 + 4 - 5^6 \cdot 78 \cdot 9)$	-146724384	$(1 + (2 + 3)^{\wedge}4) \cdot (5^6 \cdot (-7 - 8) - 9)$
-131625084	$-12 \cdot (3 + 4 + 5^6 \cdot 78 \cdot 9)$	-146890608	$(1 + (2 - 3^{\wedge}4) / 5^{\wedge}6 - 7) \cdot (8 + 9)$
-131625396	$12 \cdot (3 - (4 + 5^6 \cdot 78) \cdot 9)$	-146890642	$(-1 + (2 - 3^{\wedge}4) \cdot 5^6 \cdot 7) \cdot (8 + 9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-147002425	$1/2+(3-4^*5)/(6^*7^{\wedge}-8/9)$	-155646525	$12+3^*(4^{\wedge}5+6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-147002426	$1/-2+(3-4^*5)/(6^*7^{\wedge}-8/9)$	-155646549	$-12+3^*(4^{\wedge}5+6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149877805	$1+234^*(5^*6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155646561	$12+3^*(4^{\wedge}5-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149877806	$1^*234^*(5^*6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155646585	$-12+3^*(4^{\wedge}5-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149877807	$-1+234^*(5^*6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155648256	$1+2+3^*(456-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149882251	$1+234^*(5+6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155648257	$1^*2+3^*(456-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149882252	$1^*234^*(5+6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155648258	$1^{\wedge}2+3^*(456-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149882253	$-1+234^*(5+6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155648260	$1-2+3^*(456-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149884630	$1+234^*(5/6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155648261	$1^*-2+3^*(456-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149884631	$1^*234^*(5/6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155648394	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149884632	$-1+234^*(5/6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155648610	$(1+2)^*(345-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149887399	$1-234^*(5+6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155648967	$-12+3^*(4^*56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149887400	$-1^*234^*(5+6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155648997	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^*5^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149887401	$-1-234^*(5+6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155649103	$12+3^*(4^{\wedge}5/6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149891845	$1-234^*(5^*6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155649106	$(1+2)^*(3+4^{\wedge}5/6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149891846	$-1^*234^*(5^*6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155649124	$(1+2)^*(-3+4^{\wedge}5/6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-149891847	$-1-234^*(5^*6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155649127	$-12+3^*(4^{\wedge}5/6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-150787819	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6-7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-155649809	$1^*-2-3^*(4+5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-150866658	$(1+2)^*(3^*(4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155650127	$12-3^*(4^{\wedge}5/6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-151061055	$(1+2/3)^*(4^{\wedge}5-(6+7)^{\wedge}8)/9$	-155650130	$(1+2)^*(3-4^{\wedge}5/6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-151170651	$(1+2)^*((3^*4)^{\wedge}5^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155650148	$(1+2)^*(-3-4^{\wedge}5/6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-152797184	$(1+(2^{\wedge}-3)^{\wedge}4^*567)^*-8^{\wedge}9$	-155650151	$-12-3^*(4^{\wedge}5/6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-153541075	$1-234^*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155650257	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^*5^*-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-153541076	$-1^*234^*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155650287	$12-3^*(4^*56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-153541077	$-1-234^*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-155650644	$(-1-2)^*(345-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-154055292	$12+3^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155650860	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-154055295	$(1+2)^*(3+(4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155650993	$1^*2-3^*(456+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-154055313	$(1+2)^*(-3+(4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155650994	$1^{\wedge}2-3^*(456+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-154055316	$-12+3^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155650996	$1-2-3^*(456+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-154328108	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4)^*5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*(8+9)$	-155650997	$-1^*2-3^*(456+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-154328142	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4)^*5^{\wedge}6^*7)^*(-8-9)$	-155650998	$-1-2-3^*(456+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-154903113	$(1+2)^*((3^*4)^{\wedge}5+6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155652669	$12-3^*(4^{\wedge}5-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-154903149	$(1+2)^*((3^*4)^{\wedge}5-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155652693	$-12-3^*(4^{\wedge}5-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155087127	$(1+2)^*(3^*4/5^{\wedge}-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155652705	$12-3^*(4^{\wedge}5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155227728	$12+3^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	-155652729	$-12-3^*(4^{\wedge}5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155227776	$-12-3^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	-155653731	$(-1-2)^*(3^*456+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155295333	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155655837	$(-1-2)^*(345^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155296680	$(1+2)^*((3^*4-5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155658789	$(-1-2)^*(3^*(4^{\wedge}5-6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155321502	$(1+2)^*((3+4)/5^{\wedge}-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155658825	$(-1-2)^*(3^*4^{\wedge}5-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155347101	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^{\wedge}5^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155658861	$(-1-2)^*(3^*4^{\wedge}5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155462115	$12+3^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155658897	$(-1-2)^*(3^*(4^{\wedge}5+6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155462118	$(1+2)^*(3+4^*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155661915	$(-1-2)^*((3-4+5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155462136	$(-1-2)^*(3-4^*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155668005	$(1+2)^*((3-4^{\wedge}5)^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155462139	$-12+3^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155668047	$12-3^*(4^{\wedge}5^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155508966	$(1+2)^*(3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6)-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155668050	$(1+2)^*(3-4^{\wedge}5^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155509038	$(1+2)^*(3^*(-4+5^{\wedge}6)-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155668059	$(1-2)^*3^*(4^{\wedge}5^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155509659	$(1+2)^*((3-4-5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155668068	$(-1-2)^*(3+4^{\wedge}5^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155590560	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155668071	$-12-3^*(4^{\wedge}5^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155590596	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155668113	$(-1-2)^*((3+4^{\wedge}5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155594331	$(1+2)^*(3/4^{\wedge}-5^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155696259	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155599188	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^{\wedge}5+6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155696466	$(1+2)^*(3^*4-5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155599224	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^{\wedge}5-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155696478	$12+3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155602509	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155696526	$-12-3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155602716	$(1+2)^*(3^*4+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155696538	$(-1-2)^*(3^*4+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155602728	$12+3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155696745	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155602776	$-12-3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155700030	$(1+2)^*((-3-4)^{\wedge}5+6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155602788	$(1+2)^*(3^*-4+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155700066	$(1+2)^*((-3-4)^{\wedge}5-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155602995	$(1+2)^*(-3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155704923	$(-1-2)^*(3/4^{\wedge}-5^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155631141	$(1+2)^*((3+4^{\wedge}5)^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155708658	$(1+2)^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)+6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155631183	$12+3^*(4^{\wedge}5^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155708694	$(1+2)^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155631186	$(1+2)^*(3+4^{\wedge}5^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155789595	$(-1-2)^*((3-4-5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155631195	$(-1+2)^*3^*(4^{\wedge}5^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155790216	$(1+2)^*(3^*(4-5^{\wedge}6)-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155631204	$(-1-2)^*(3-4^{\wedge}5^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155790288	$(-1-2)^*(3^*(4+5^{\wedge}6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155631207	$-12+3^*(4^{\wedge}5^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155837115	$12-3^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155631249	$(-1-2)^*((3-4^{\wedge}5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155837118	$(1+2)^*(3-4^*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155637339	$(1+2)^*((3-4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155837136	$(-1-2)^*(3+4^*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155640357	$(1+2)^*(3^*(4^{\wedge}5+6)-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155837139	$-12-3^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155640393	$(1+2)^*(3^*4^{\wedge}5+6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155952153	$(-1-2)^*((3+4)^{\wedge}5^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155640429	$(1+2)^*(3^*4^{\wedge}5-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-155977752	$(-1-2)^*((3+4)^*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155640465	$(1+2)^*(3^*(4^{\wedge}5-6)-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-156002574	$(-1-2)^*((3^*4-5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155643417	$(1+2)^*(345^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-156003921	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-155645523	$(1+2)^*(3^*456-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-156071466	$(1+2)^*(3^*4-(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-156071478	$12+3*(4-(5^6+7^8)*9)$	-203872903	$(1-234)*(5^6*7^8-9)$
-156071526	$-12-3*(4+(5^6+7^8)*9)$	-203877097	$(1-234)*(5^6*7^8+9)$
-156071538	$(-1-2)*(3*4+(5^6+7^8)*9)$	-204067095	$12+3^4*(5-(6^7-8)*9)$
-156212127	$(1+2)*(3*4/-5^6-6-7^8*9)$	-204067119	$-12+3^4*(5-(6^7-8)*9)$
-156396105	$(-1-2)*((3*4)^5-6+7^8*9)$	-204067905	$12-3^4*(5+(6^7-8)*9)$
-156396141	$(-1-2)*((3*4)^5+6+7^8*9)$	-204067929	$-12-3^4*(5+(6^7-8)*9)$
-157243938	$12-3*((4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	-204078759	$12+3^4*(5-(6^7+8)*9)$
-157243941	$(1+2)*(3-(4+5)^6-7^8*9)$	-204078783	$-12+3^4*(5-(6^7+8)*9)$
-157243959	$(-1-2)*(3+(4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	-204079569	$12-3^4*(5+(6^7+8)*9)$
-157243962	$-12-3*((4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	-204079593	$-12-3^4*(5+(6^7+8)*9)$
-159457077	$(1-2/3^4-4*(5^6*7-8))*9$	-204747893	$1-234*(5^6*7^8-9)$
-159457095	$(-1-2/3^4-4*(5^6*7-8))*9$	-204747895	$-1-234*(5^6*7^8-9)$
-159468660	$1-2/((3/45)^6/7)+89$	-204752105	$1-234*(5^6*7^8+9)$
-159468662	$-1-2/((3/45)^6/7)+89$	-204752107	$-1-234*(5^6*7^8+9)$
-159468838	$1-2/((3/45)^6/7)-89$	-205622885	$(-1-234)*(5^6*7^8-9)$
-159468840	$-1-2/((3/45)^6/7)-89$	-205627115	$(-1-234)*(5^6*7^8+9)$
-159480405	$(1-2/3^4-4*(5^6*7+8))*9$	-207530884	$12^3+4*(56-7^8*9)$
-159480423	$(-1-2/3^4-4*(5^6*7+8))*9$	-207531332	$12^3-4*(56+7^8*9)$
-160128603	$(-1-2)*((3*4)^5*6+7^8*9)$	-207532588	$1+23+4*(56-7^8*9)$
-160432596	$(-1-2)*(3*(4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	-207532589	$1*23+4*(56-7^8*9)$
-161790825	$(1-(2*3)^4)*((5^6-7)*8-9)$	-207532904	$-1-23-4*(5+6+7^8*9)$
-161814135	$(1-(2*3)^4)*((5^6-7)*8+9)$	-207533083	$-1*23-4*(56+7^8*9)$
-161935865	$(1-(2*3)^4)*((5^6+7)*8-9)$	-207533084	$-1-23-4*(56+7^8*9)$
-161959175	$(1-(2*3)^4)*((5^6+7)*8+9)$	-207534340	$-12^3+4*(56-7^8*9)$
-162040695	$(1+(2*3)^4)*((5^6-7)*-8+9)$	-207534788	$-12^3-4*(56+7^8*9)$
-162064041	$(1+(2*3)^4)*((5^6-7)*-8-9)$	-212624892	$(1+2)^3*(4-5^6*7^8*9)$
-162185959	$(1+(2*3)^4)*((5^6+7)*-8+9)$	-212625108	$(-1-2)^3*(4+5^6*7^8*9)$
-162209305	$(1+(2*3)^4)*((5^6+7)*-8-9)$	-214156162	$(1-23)*(-4+5^6*7^8*9)$
-162620691	$(1-2*(3^4(4*5-6)-7))*8+9$	-214156338	$(1-23)*(4+5^6*7^8*9)$
-162620725	$(-1-2*(3^4(4*5-6)-7))*8+9$	-219651849	$-1/2*((3*(4+5))^6+7^8*9)$
-162621167	$(1-2*(3^4(4*5-6)+7))*8+9$	-223543296	$(1+2/3-4^4-5/6*7)*-8^9$
-162621201	$(-1-2*(3^4(4*5-6)+7))*8+9$	-223696207	$(1+2/3)*(4-5^6(6-7)-8^9)$
-164061996	$(1-(2+3)^4(4+5)/6)*7^8*9$	-223882348	$(1+23*(4-5^6*7))*89$
-164063004	$(1+(2+3)^4(4+5)/6)*7^8*9$	-223882436	$1+23*(4-5^6*7)*89$
-164102448	$(-1-2)/(3^4+5)^6(6+7-8-9)$	-223882438	$-1+23*(4-5^6*7)*89$
-164296828	$1/2-(3-(4-5)/6)*7^8*9$	-223882526	$(-1+23*(4-5^6*7))*89$
-164296829	$1/-2-(3-(4-5)/6)*7^8*9$	-223890532	$1+23*(4-5^6*7)*89$
-164531190	$(-12+3*(4-5^6*7^8*9))$	-223890534	$-1+23*(4-5^6*7)*89$
-164531310	$(-12-3*(4+5^6*7^8*9))$	-223890716	$1-23*(4+5^6*7)*89$
-164607579	$(-1-2)*((3+4+5)^6+7^8*9)$	-223890718	$-1-23*(4+5^6*7)*89$
-168232527	$12-3*(4^4(5+6)+7^8*9)$	-223898724	$(1-23*(4+5^6*7))*89$
-168232530	$(1+2)*(3-4^4(5+6)-7^8*9)$	-223898812	$1-23*(4+5^6*7)*89$
-168232548	$(-1-2)*(3+4^4(5+6)+7^8*9)$	-223898814	$-1-23*(4+5^6*7)*89$
-168232551	$-12-3*(4^4(5+6)+7^8*9)$	-223898902	$(-1-23*(4+5^6*7))*89$
-182168343	$(1-2/3^4-4*(5^6-7)*8)*9$	-226409976	$(1-2/3^4-4*5)*(6^7-8*9)$
-182168361	$(-1-2/3^4-4*(5^6-7)*8)*9$	-226454471	$(1-2*3^4*5)*(6^7-8-9)$
-182331639	$(1-2/3^4-4*(5^6+7)*8)*9$	-226467415	$(1-2*3^4*5)*(6^7+8-9)$
-182331657	$(-1-2/3^4-4*(5^6+7)*8)*9$	-226469033	$(1-2*3^4*5)*(6^7-8+9)$
-184473356	$12*(3+4*(5-6*7^8/9))$	-226481977	$(1-2*3^4*5)*(6^7+8+9)$
-184473428	$-12*(3-4*(5-6*7^8/9))$	-226526472	$(1-2/3^4-4*5)*(6^7+8*9)$
-184473620	$12-(3+45)*6*7^8/9$	-226747981	$1-2*(3^4*5*6^7-89)$
-184473644	$-12-(3+45)*6*7^8/9$	-226747983	$-1-2*(3^4*5*6^7-89)$
-184473836	$12*(3-4*(5+6*7^8/9))$	-226748339	$-1-2*(3^4*5*6^7+89)$
-184473908	$-12*(3+4*(5+6*7^8/9))$	-226969704	$(-1-2/3^4-4*5)*(6^7-8*9)$
-184953036	$(1-(23-4)*5^6*7)*89$	-227014309	$(-1-2*3^4*5)*(6^7-8-9)$
-188839296	$12^3*(4-5^6*7+89)$	-227027285	$(-1-2*3^4*5)*(6^7+8-9)$
-188853120	$-12^3*(4+5^6*7-89)$	-227028096	$(1+2*3^4*5)*6^7/(8-9)$
-188999991	$(1-2*3^4/(5^6-6/7/8))*9$	-227028907	$(-1-2*3^4*5)*(6^7-8+9)$
-189000009	$(1+2*3^4*5^6*7^8)*-9$	-227041883	$(-1-2*3^4*5)*(6^7+8+9)$
-189146880	$12^3*(4-5^6*7-89)$	-227086488	$(-1-2/3^4-4*5)*(6^7+8*9)$
-189160704	$-12^3*(4+5^6*7+89)$	-228062334	$(-1-2)*((3-4^5)^6+7^8*9)$
-193398363	$(1+2*(3^4-4^4(5+6)-7^8*9))$	-229042817	$(1-(2^3)^4/5)*(6^7+8-9)$
-194637253	$1-2*(3^4^5-6+7^8*9)$	-229602687	$(1+(2^3)^4/5)*(-6^7-8+9)$
-194637255	$-1-2*(3^4^5-6+7^8*9)$	-230326893	$(1-234*(5^6*7-8))*9$
-194637277	$1-2*(3^4^5+6+7^8*9)$	-230326901	$1-234*(5^6*7-8)*9$
-194637279	$-1-2*(3^4^5+6+7^8*9)$	-230326903	$-1-234*(5^6*7-8)*9$
-198885634	$1/2-(3+4*5)/(6/(7^8*9))$	-230326911	$(-1-234*(5^6*7-8))*9$
-198885635	$-1/2-(3+4*5)/(6/(7^8*9))$	-230360589	$(1-234*(5^6*7+8))*9$
-201542247	$(1+2*(3^4-5/6^7-7)*8)*9$	-230360597	$1-234*(5^6*7+8)*9$
-201542265	$(-1+2*(3^4-5/6^7-7)*8)*9$	-230360599	$-1-234*(5^6*7+8)*9$
-201565575	$(1-2*(3^4+5/6^7-7)*8)*9$	-230360607	$(-1-234*(5^6*7+8))*9$
-201565593	$(-1-2*(3^4+5/6^7-7)*8)*9$	-230591572	$12*(3-4*(5/6/7^8-8-9))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-230591644	$12^*(3-4^5/(6/(7^8-9)))$	-268426399	$-1+2^*(3^4*56-7-8^9)$
-230591716	$-12^*(3+4^5/(6/(7^8-9)))$	-268433539	$-1+2^*((3^4+56)*7-8^9)$
-230592436	$12^*(3-4^*(5/6/7^8-8+9))$	-268434513	$-1+2^*(3^4*5+67-8^9)$
-230592508	$-12^*(3+4^*(5/6/7^8-8+9))$	-268434781	$-1+2^*(3^4*5-67-8^9)$
-233473221	$1/2^*(3^4*(5*6-7^8)+9)$	-268436131	$1-2^*(3^4*5-67+8^9)$
-233624904	$(1+23)^*(4-5^6*7^8*9)$	-268436399	$1-2^*(3^4*5+67+8^9)$
-233625096	$(-1-23)^*(4+5^6*7^8*9)$	-268437373	$1-2^*((3^4+56)*7+8^9)$
-235064105	$12-((3^4)^5*6+7)/89$	-268444513	$1-2^*(3^4*56-7+8^9)$
-235064129	$-12-((3^4)^5*6+7)/89$	-268444515	$-1-2^*(3^4*56-7+8^9)$
-237999983	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))^5*6*7^8*(8+9)$	-268444541	$1-2^*(3^4*56+7+8^9)$
-238000017	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))^5*6*7^8*(8+9)$	-268444543	$-1-2^*(3^4*56+7+8^9)$
-241312412	$(1-23)^*(4+5^6*7^8*9)$	-268444549	$1+2^*(3^4*(5-67)-8^9)$
-241312588	$(1-23)^*(4+5^6*7^8*9)$	-268445501	$-1+2^*(3^4*(5-67)-8^9)$
-241780032	$12^{\wedge}3*(4-5^6-78)^9$	-268445639	$1-2^*((3^4-5)*67+8^9)$
-241793856	$-12^{\wedge}3*(4+(5^6-78)^9)$	-268445641	$-1-2^*((3^4-5)*67+8^9)$
-244206144	$12^{\wedge}3*(4-5^6+78)^9$	-268446979	$1-2^*((3^4+5)*67+8^9)$
-244219968	$-12^{\wedge}3*(4+(5^6+78)^9)$	-268446981	$-1-2^*((3^4+5)*67+8^9)$
-244994301	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4))^5*6^{\wedge}(-7+8+9)$	-268447119	$1-2^*(3^4*(5+67)+8^9)$
-247886416	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5)/6/-7^8-8+9)$	-268447121	$-1-2^*(3^4*(5+67)+8^9)$
-247886470	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5)/6/-7^8-8-9)$	-268489725	$1-2^*(3^4*5*67+8^9)$
-249039403	$1/(2+3)-4/(5/6*7^8-8)^9$	-268489727	$-1-2^*(3^4*5*67+8^9)$
-249261493	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3*(4+5)))^*(6/7-8+9)$	-268498959	$1-2^*(3^4*56*7+8^9)$
-250192754	$(1-2^*(3^4/5+6))^*(7^8+9)$	-268498961	$-1-2^*(3^4*56*7+8^9)$
-252280413	$(1+23^*(4-5^6*78))^9$	-268527309	$1-2^*(3^4*567+8^9)$
-252280421	$1+23^*(4-5^6*78)^9$	-268527310	$-1+2^*(3^4*567+8^9)$
-252280423	$-1+23^*(4-5^6*78)^9$	-268527311	$-1-2^*(3^4*567+8^9)$
-252280431	$(-1+23^*(4-5^6*78))^9$	-268654137	$1+2^*(34-5^6*7-8^9)$
-252281157	$1+23^*(4-5^6*78)^9$	-268654139	$-1+2^*(34-5^6*7-8^9)$
-252281159	$-1+23^*(4-5^6*78)^9$	-268654273	$1-2^*(34+5^6*7+8^9)$
-252281341	$1-23^*(4+5^6*78)^9$	-268654275	$-1-2^*(34+5^6*7+8^9)$
-252281343	$-1-23^*(4+5^6*78)^9$	-269792687	$-1/(2+3)+(4/5-6)*7^8*9$
-252282069	$(1-23^*(4+5^6*78))^9$	-269999899	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^6)^{\wedge}7+89$
-252282077	$1-23^*(4+5^6*78)^9$	-269999923	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^6)^{\wedge}7+89$
-252282079	$-1-23^*(4+5^6*78)^9$	-270000077	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^6)^{\wedge}7-89$
-252282087	$(-1-23^*(4+5^6*78))^9$	-270000101	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5^6)^{\wedge}7-89$
-254313151	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}(4*5-6))/(7+8+9)$	-272091864	$12^*(3^4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)+89)$
-254803989	$-12-(3+45)^{\wedge}(6+7-8)-9$	-272094000	$12^*(3^4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)-89)$
-255300564	$-12^*(3^4-5)^6*7^8-89$	-272101584	$-12^*(3^4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)-89)$
-255302700	$-12^*((3^4-5)^6*7^8+89)$	-272103720	$-12^*(3^4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)+89)$
-259413764	$1+(2+3)^*(456-7^8*9)$	-276686256	$12^{\wedge}3/4*(56-7^8/9)$
-259413765	$(1+2+3)^*(456-7^8*9)$	-276734640	$12^{\wedge}3/4*(-56-7^8/9)$
-259413766	$-1+(2+3)^*(456-7^8*9)$	-278686192	$1-23^*((4*5)^6-7^8*9)$
-259418324	$1-(2+3)^*(456+7^8*9)$	-278686194	$-1-23^*((4*5)^6-7^8*9)$
-259418325	$(1-2*3)^*(456+7^8*9)$	-280169010	$(1+2)^*(3^4/5*(6-7^8)+9)$
-259418326	$-1-(2+3)^*(456+7^8*9)$	-280169064	$(1+2)^*(3^4/5*(6-7^8)-9)$
-261722374	$(-1-2^*(3^4/5+6))^*(7^8+9)$	-282475222	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3-(4-5-6)^{\wedge}(-7+8+9)$
-262828036	$(1-(23+4)^5*6*7^8)^89$	-282475276	$(-1-2)^{\wedge}3-(4-5-6)^{\wedge}(-7+8+9)$
-262828214	$(1+(23+4)^5*6*7^8)^89$	-288240031	$1-2^*((3^4-56)*7^8-9)$
-263249904	$(1+23)^*(4-5^6*78)^9$	-288240033	$-1-2^*((3^4-56)*7^8-9)$
-263250096	$(-1-23)^*(4+5^6*78)^9$	-288240049	$1+(2*3-456)*7^8/9$
-268216637	$1+2^*(34+5^6*7-8^9)$	-288240051	$-1+(2*3-456)*7^8/9$
-268216639	$-1+2^*(34+5^6*7-8^9)$	-288240067	$1-2^*((3^4-56)*7^8+9)$
-268216773	$1-2^*(34-5^6*7+8^9)$	-288240069	$-1-2^*((3^4-56)*7^8+9)$
-268216775	$-1-2^*(34-5^6*7+8^9)$	-288458040	$(-1-2)^*((3+4*5)^6-7^8*9)$
-268343601	$1+2^*(3^4*567-8^9)$	-288892884	$-12^*((3^4+5)*6^{\wedge}7-89)$
-268343602	$1*2^*(3^4*567-8^9)$	-288895020	$-12^*((3^4+5)*6^{\wedge}7+89)$
-268343603	$-1+2^*(3^4*567-8^9)$	-294004681	$(1+2/3+4)^*(5*6-7^8*9)$
-268371951	$1+2^*(3^4*56*7-8^9)$	-294005021	$(1+2/3+4)^*(5*6-7^8*9)$
-268371953	$-1+2^*(3^4*56*7-8^9)$	-297464196	$(1+2^*(3+4/5))^*6*(7^8+9)$
-268381185	$1+2^*(3^4*5*67-8^9)$	-298539108	$12^*(3^4*5-6^{\wedge}7)*89$
-268381187	$-1+2^*(3^4*5*67-8^9)$	-298966788	$12^*(3^4*5-6^{\wedge}7*89)$
-268423791	$1+2^*(3^4*(5+67)-8^9)$	-298976508	$-12^*(3^4*5+6^{\wedge}7*89)$
-268423793	$-1+2^*(3^4*(5+67)-8^9)$	-299404188	$-12^*(3^4*5+6^{\wedge}7)*89$
-268423931	$1+2^*((3^4+5)*67-8^9)$	-302210835	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)*7-8^9)$
-268423933	$-1+2^*((3^4+5)*67-8^9)$	-302652052	$1/2-(3+4)^5/(6*7^8-8/9)$
-268425271	$1+2^*((3^4-5)*67-8^9)$	-302652053	$-1/2-(3+4)^5/(6*7^8-8/9)$
-268425273	$-1+2^*((3^4-5)*67-8^9)$	-303503970	$(1-(2*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^6*(7+8)-9)$
-268425411	$1-2^*(3^4*(5-67)+8^9)$	-303527280	$(1-(2*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^6*(7+8)+9)$
-268425413	$-1-2^*(3^4*(5-67)+8^9)$	-303749943	$(1+(2^{\wedge}(3+4))-(5*6)^{\wedge}7)/8)^9$
-268426369	$1+2^*(3^4*56+7-8^9)$	-303750057	$(1+(2^{\wedge}(3+4))+(5*6)^{\wedge}7)/8)^9$
-268426371	$-1+2^*(3^4*56+7-8^9)$	-303972702	$(1+(2*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^6*(-7-8)+9)$
-268426397	$1+2^*(3^4*56-7-8^9)$	-303996048	$(1+(2*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^6*(-7-8)-9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-304570351	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3+4+5)*6^{\wedge}7)*(8+9)$	-363189589	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4^{\wedge}5-6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-304570385	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3+4+5)*6^{\wedge}7)*(-8-9)$	-363189673	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4^{\wedge}5+6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-311296517	$1+2*3*(456-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-363193215	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4^{\wedge}5/6+7^{\wedge}8)*9$
-311296518	$(1+2+3)*(456-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-363225471	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4^{\wedge}5*6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-311296519	$-1+2*3*(456-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-363291810	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-311301989	$1-2*3*(456+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-363291866	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-311301990	$(1+2+3)*(-456-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-363619963	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-311301991	$-1-2*3*(456+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-364166810	$(1+2*3)*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)*9)$
-319946455	$1/2-(3+4-5/6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$	-364166866	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)*9)$
-319946456	$1/2-(3+4-5/6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$	-366902550	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-322825832	$12*(3-45)*(-6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-368943808	$12*(3+45)*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-322831880	$12*(3-45)*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-368950720	$-12*(3+45)*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-326637184	$(-1-2/(3+4)*5)*(6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-377552896	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3*4)*5^{\wedge}6-7)/8^{\wedge}-9$
-330429696	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4+5)*6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-378011648	$(1-2^{\wedge}(-3*4)*5^{\wedge}6+7)/8^{\wedge}-9$
-332859267	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-382941495	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7-8)*9$
-332859483	$(-1-2)^{\wedge}3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*789)$	-382941513	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7-8)*9$
-333822335	$(1+2*3)*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-382952295	$(1-2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7-8))*9$
-334627521	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7)-8^{\wedge}9)$	-382952313	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7-8)*9$
-334629951	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7)+8^{\wedge}9)$	-382952583	$(1-2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7+8))*9$
-338827776	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-382952601	$(-1-2*((3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7+8))*9$
-340120269	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5*6^{\wedge}7-8)-9)$	-382963383	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7+8)*9$
-340120323	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5*6^{\wedge}7-8)+9)$	-382963401	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7+8)*9$
-340122189	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6^{\wedge}7-8-9)$	-383936346	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4/5+6)*(-7^{\wedge}8-9)$
-340122237	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6^{\wedge}7+8-9)$	-385471455	$12+3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7*(8+9))$
-340122243	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6^{\wedge}7+8-9)$	-385471479	$-12+3^{\wedge}4*(5-6^{\wedge}7*(8+9))$
-340122291	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6^{\wedge}7+8+9)$	-385472265	$12-3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7*(8+9))$
-340124157	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5*6^{\wedge}7+8)-9)$	-385472289	$-12-3^{\wedge}4*(5+6^{\wedge}7*(8+9))$
-340124211	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5*6^{\wedge}7+8)+9)$	-386201085	$1-2*(3^{\wedge}4(5-6+7)/8-9)$
-345887763	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5/6/7^{\wedge}8-8))^9$	-386201123	$-1-2*(3^{\wedge}4(5-6+7)/8+9)$
-345887781	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3*(4-5/6/7^{\wedge}8-8))^9$	-392006432	$12*(3-(45+6)*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-345887997	$(1+2*(3-4*5/6/7^{\wedge}8-8))^9$	-392006504	$-12*(3+(45+6)*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-345888123	$(1+2*(3+4*5/6/7^{\wedge}8-8))^9$	-392542591	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-345888339	$(1-2^{\wedge}3*(4+5/6/7^{\wedge}8-8))^9$	-394312491	$(1+2)*(3+4/5)*6*(7^{\wedge}8-9)$
-345888357	$(1+2^{\wedge}3*(4+5/6/7^{\wedge}8-8))^9$	-394874991	$(1-(2+34)*5^{\wedge}6*78)^9$
-345990236	$(-12-3*(45^{\wedge}6+7)/8)/9$	-394875009	$(1+(2+34)*5^{\wedge}6*78)^9$
-347649615	$12-3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-395507812	$1/2-3^{\wedge}4*5/6*(7+8)^{\wedge}9$
-347649618	$(1+2)*(3-(4*5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-395507813	$-1/2-3^{\wedge}4*5/6*(7+8)^{\wedge}9$
-347649636	$(-1-2)*(3+(4*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-395538255	$(1-(2*3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7-8)*9$
-347649639	$-12-3*((4*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-395538273	$(1+(2*3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7-8)*9$
-350437411	$(1-(2+34)*5^{\wedge}6*7)*89$	-395560863	$(1-(2*3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7+8)*9$
-350437589	$(1+(2+34)*5^{\wedge}6*7)*89$	-395560881	$(1+(2*3^{\wedge}4-5)*6^{\wedge}7+8)*9$
-351562491	$(1-(2+3)*4/5^{\wedge}(6-7-8))^9$	-398443776	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4-4*5)*6^{\wedge}7-8)^9$
-351562509	$(1+(2+3)*4/5^{\wedge}(6-7-8))^9$	-398464512	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-4*5)*6^{\wedge}7+8)^9$
-352805821	$1/(2+3)-(4/5+6)*7^{\wedge}8*9$	-398715684	$(1+2)*(3*4/5^{\wedge}6*7-8)^9$
-359462376	$(1+2*3)*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-398854608	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)-8^{\wedge}9)$
-362198060	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3)*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)*9)$	-398858010	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7)-8^{\wedge}9)$
-362198116	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)*9)$	-401340672	$12+3*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-362387884	$1/2-3^{\wedge}4/(5*6/(7+8^{\wedge}9))$	-401340675	$(1+2)*(3+4*5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-362387885	$-1/2-3^{\wedge}4/(5*6)*(7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-401340693	$(-1-2)*(3-4*5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
-362744963	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(-4*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-401340696	$-12+3*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363073060	$(1+2*3)*(4+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-401668773	$(1+2)*(3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7)-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363073116	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4-5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-401668845	$(1+2)*(3*(-4+5^{\wedge}6*7)-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363139455	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4-5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-401770464	$-12*(3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)*7+89)$
-363171711	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3)*(4^{\wedge}5/6-7^{\wedge}8)*9$	-401812161	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5+6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363175253	$(1+2*3)*(4^{\wedge}5+6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-401814591	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5-6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$
-363175337	$(1+2*3)*(4^{\wedge}5-6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402323358	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6)*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363179271	$(1+2*3)*(456-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402324816	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363181623	$(1+2*3)*(4*5*6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402325023	$(1+2)*(3*4+5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363182059	$12+(3+4)*(56-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402325035	$12+3*(4+5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363182155	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(-4*(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402325083	$-12-3*(4-5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
-363182281	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4-5*6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402325095	$(1+2)*(-3*4+5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363182358	$(1+2*3)*(4+5+6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402325302	$(1+2)*(-3^{\wedge}4+5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363182365	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(-4*5+6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402326760	$(-1-2)*((3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}6)*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
-363182414	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4-5-6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402515403	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5^{\wedge}6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363182512	$(1+2*3)*(4-5-6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402601344	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363182561	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4*5-6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402602154	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5*6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363182568	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4+5+6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402634473	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6)*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363182645	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4*5+6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402637389	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*5*(6+7)-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363182771	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4*(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402641763	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5+6*7)-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363182867	$-12-(3+4)*(56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402642348	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4+5)*6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363183303	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(4*5*6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402644193	$(1+2)*(3^{\wedge}4*(5*6+7)-8^{\wedge}9)$
-363185655	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)*(456+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-402644553	$(1+2)*((3^{\wedge}4*5+6)*7-8^{\wedge}9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-402644805	$(1+2)^*((3^4*5-6)^*7-8^9)$	-406862592	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-4+5)^*6^7+8^9)$
-402645873	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5^6+7-8^9)$	-407346816	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-4*(5^6)^7-8^9)$
-402645915	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5^6-7-8^9)$	-408127725	$(1+2*3^4*(5-6^7+8))^*9$
-402647595	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7)-8^9)$	-408127743	$(-1+2*3^4*(5-6^7+8))^*9$
-402648810	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5+6+7)-8^9)$	-408139245	$(1+2*(3^4*(5-6^7)+8))^*9$
-402649830	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5)^*(6+7)-8^9)$	-408139263	$(-1+2*(3^4*(5-6^7)+8))^*9$
-402650220	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5)^*(6+7)-8^9)$	-408139533	$(1+2*(3^4*(5-6^7)-8))^*9$
-402650490	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5+6)+7-8^9)$	-408139551	$(-1+2*(3^4*(5-6^7)-8))^*9$
-402650532	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5+6)-7-8^9)$	-408142305	$(1-2*3^4*(5+6^7-8))^*9$
-402650853	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5^6)^*7-8^9)$	-408142323	$(-1-2*3^4*(5+6^7-8))^*9$
-402651252	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5+6)^*7-8^9)$	-408151053	$(1+2*3^4*(5-6^7-8))^*9$
-402651615	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5)^*6+7-8^9)$	-408151071	$(-1+2*3^4*(5-6^7-8))^*9$
-402651657	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5)^*6-7-8^9)$	-408153825	$(1-2*(3^4*(5+6^7)-8))^*9$
-402651714	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5-6)^*7-8^9)$	-408153843	$(-1-2*(3^4*(5+6^7)-8))^*9$
-402651843	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5+6^*7-8^9)$	-408154113	$(1-2*(3^4*(5+6^7)+8))^*9$
-402651930	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5+6+7-8^9)$	-408154131	$(-1-2*(3^4*(5+6^7)+8))^*9$
-402651966	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5-6+7-8^9)$	-408165633	$(1-2*3^4*(5+6^7+8))^*9$
-402651969	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5+(6-7)^*8^9)$	-408165651	$(-1-2*3^4*(5+6^7+8))^*9$
-402652212	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5+6-7)-8^9)$	-412760396	$(-12+3/45)^*6*(7^8+9)$
-402652883	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5)/6^*7-8^9)$	-415062023	$1+2^3*(456-7^8*9)$
-402652918	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5)/6^*7-8^9)$	-415062024	$1+2^3*(456-7^8*9)$
-402653450	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5)/-6^*7-8^9)$	-415062025	$-1+2^3*(456-7^8*9)$
-402653485	$(1+2)^*((3^4+5)/-6^*7-8^9)$	-415065217	$1+2*(3+4*(56-7^8*9))$
-402654156	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5+6-7)+8^9)$	-415065219	$-1+2*(3+4*(56-7^8*9))$
-402654399	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5/(6-7)-8^9)$	-415065229	$1-2*(3-4*(56-7^8*9))$
-402654402	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5-6+7+8^9)$	-415066115	$-1+2*(3-4*(56+7^8*9))$
-402654438	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5+6+7+8^9)$	-415066125	$1-2*(3+4*(56+7^8*9))$
-402654525	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5+6^*7+8^9)$	-415066127	$-1-2*(3+4*(56+7^8*9))$
-402654654	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-5-6)^*7+8^9)$	-415069319	$1-2^3*(456+7^8*9)$
-402654711	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5)^*6-7+8^9)$	-415069320	$-1+2^3*(456+7^8*9)$
-402654753	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5)^*6+7+8^9)$	-415069321	$-1-2^3*(456+7^8*9)$
-402655116	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5+6)^*7+8^9)$	-417372244	$(12+3/45)^*-6*(7^8+9)$
-402655515	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5^6)^*7+8^9)$	-420350373	$(1+2)^*(-3/(4^5)^6+7^8*9)$
-402655836	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5+6)-7+8^9)$	-420731775	$(1-(2*3^4+5)^*(6^7-8))^*9$
-402655878	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5+6)+7+8^9)$	-420731793	$(1+(2*3^4+5)^*(6^7-8))^*-9$
-402656148	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-5)^*(6+7)+8^9)$	-420755823	$(1-(2*3^4+5)^*(6^7+8))^*9$
-402656538	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5)^*(6+7)+8^9)$	-420755841	$(1+(2*3^4+5)^*(6^7+8))^*-9$
-402657558	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5+6+7)+8^9)$	-421653926	$1-(2^3-3)^4*5^6*7+8^9$
-402658773	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7)+8^9)$	-421653928	$-1-(2^3-3)^4*5^6*7+8^9$
-402660453	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^6-7+8^9)$	-421654104	$1-(2^3-3)^4*5^6*7-8^9$
-402660495	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^6+7+8^9)$	-421654106	$-1-(2^3-3)^4*5^6*7-8^9$
-402661563	$(-1-2)^*((3^4*5-6)^*7+8^9)$	-433340775	$(-1-2*((3^4+5)^*6^7-8))^*9$
-402661815	$(-1-2)^*((3^4*5+6)^*7+8^9)$	-433340793	$(-1-2*((3^4+5)^*6^7-8))^*9$
-402662175	$(1+2)^*(3^4*(5-6^*7)-8^9)$	-433341063	$(1-2*((3^4+5)^*6^7+8))^*9$
-402664020	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5)^*6^*7+8^9)$	-433341081	$(-1-2*((3^4+5)^*6^7+8))^*9$
-402664605	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5+6^*7)+8^9)$	-441458669	$1-2*(3^4*5^6-7^8*9)$
-402668979	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^*(6+7)+8^9)$	-441458671	$-1-2*(3^4*5^6-7^8*9)$
-402671895	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5+6)^*7+8^9)$	-446195649	$(-1-2*(3+4/5))^*(6+7^8*9)$
-402704214	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^6*7+8^9)$	-446410440	$(-1-2/3)/((4+5)^6-6/7/8/9)$
-402705024	$(-1-2)^*(3^4-4*5^6+7+8^9)$	-447595785	$(1-(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7-8^9)$
-402790965	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5^6+7+8^9)$	-447814391	$(1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7+8^9)$
-402979608	$(1+2)^*((3^4-5^6)^*7-8^9)$	-447821010	$(1-(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7-8-9)$
-402981066	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6*7-8^9)$	-447886530	$(1-(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7+8-9)$
-402981273	$(1+2)^*(3^4-5^6*7-8^9)$	-447886985	$(1-(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7-8/9)$
-402981285	$12+3*(4-5^6*7-8^9)$	-447894265	$(1-(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7+8/9)$
-402981333	$-12-3*(4+5^6*7+8^9)$	-447894720	$(1-(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7-8+9)$
-402981345	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+5^6*7+8^9)$	-447960240	$(1-(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7+8+9)$
-402981552	$(-1-2)^*(3^4+5^6*7+8^9)$	-448039726	$(1+2^3(3^4))^*(5^6*7+8+9)$
-402983010	$(-1-2)^*((3^4+5^6)^*7+8^9)$	-448105278	$(1+2^3(3^4))^*(5^6*7-8+9)$
-403491777	$(1+2)^*(3^4*5-6^7-8^9)$	-448113472	$(1+2^3(3^4))^*(5^6*7+8-9)$
-403494207	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*5+6^7+8^9)$	-448179024	$(1+2^3(3^4))^*(5^6*7-8-9)$
-403637523	$(1+2)^*(3*(4-5^6*7)-8^9)$	-448185465	$(1-(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7+8^9)$
-403637595	$(-1-2)^*(3*(4+5^6*7)+8^9)$	-448404359	$(1+(2^3)^4)^*(5^6*7-8^9)$
-403965675	$(1+2)^*(3-4*5^6*7-8^9)$	-449599039	$(1-2/3^4(-4^5+6))^*(7^8-9)$
-403965693	$(-1-2)^*(3+4*5^6*7+8^9)$	-449599133	$(-1-2*3^4(4^5-6))^*(7^8-9)$
-403965696	$-12-3*(4^5*6^*7+8^9)$	-449654477	$1-2*(345+6)^*7^8/9$
-406418470	$1/2-(3+4+5/6)^*7^8*9$	-449654479	$-1-2*(345+6)^*7^8/9$
-406418471	$1/-2-(3+4+5/6)^*7^8*9$	-461184044	$12*(3-(4+56)^*7^8/9)$
-406448358	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6-7)+8^9)$	-461184116	$-12*(3+(4+56)^*7^8/9)$
-406451760	$(-1-2)^*(3^4*(5^6+7)+8^9)$	-465683220	$(1+2^3)^*(4+(5^6-7^8)^*9)$
-406590684	$(-1-2)^*(3^4/5^6-6^*7+8^9)$	-465683292	$(1+2^3)^*(-4+(5^6-7^8)^*9)$
-406841856	$(1+2)^*((3^4-4-5)^*6^7-8^9)$	-466478592	$(-1-2)^*((3^4-5)^*6^7+8^9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-466943604	$12+3^4*(56-7^8+9)$	-544194396	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5-6^7*8)-9)$
-466943628	$-12+3^4*(56-7^8+9)$	-544196772	$(-1-2)*(3^4*(5+6^7*8)-9)$
-466945062	$12+3^4*(56-7^8-9)$	-544196826	$(-1-2)*(3^4*(5+6^7*8)+9)$
-466945086	$-12+3^4*(56-7^8-9)$	-544205277	$(-1-2)*(3^4*(5+6^7*8)^*8-9)$
-466948084	$1/2+3^4*(5/6-7^8+9)$	-544205331	$(-1-2)*(3^4*(5+6^7*8)^*8+9)$
-466948085	$-1/2+3^4*(5/6-7^8+9)$	-545994384	$(1-(2+3)^4)*(5^6*7^8-9)$
-466948219	$1/2-3^4*(5/6+7^8-9)$	-546005616	$(1-(2+3)^4)*(5^6*7^8+9)$
-466948220	$-1/2-3^4*(5/6+7^8-9)$	-547744366	$(1+(2+3)^4)*(5^6*7^8+9)$
-466949542	$1/2+3^4*(5/6-7^8-9)$	-547755634	$(1+(2+3)^4)*(5^6*7^8-9)$
-466949543	$-1/2+3^4*(5/6-7^8-9)$	-552136625	$(1+2/3)*(4+(5+6)^7)*(-8-9)$
-466949677	$1/2-3^4*(5/6+7^8+9)$	-569173056	$(1+(2-3^4*(4^5-6))^*7)*(8+9)$
-466949678	$-1/2-3^4*(5/6+7^8+9)$	-569173090	$(-1+(2-3^4*(4^5-6))^*7)*(8+9)$
-466952676	$12-3^4*(56+7^8-9)$	-569173532	$(1-(2+3^4*(4^5-6))^*7)*(8+9)$
-466952700	$-12-3^4*(56+7^8-9)$	-569173566	$(1+(2+3^4*(4^5-6))^*7)*(-8-9)$
-466954134	$12-3^4*(56+7^8+9)$	-569434232	$(1+(2-3^4*(5+6))^*7^8)/9$
-466954158	$-12-3^4*(56+7^8+9)$	-570696777	$(1-(2-(3+4)^{-5})^6)^*7^8*9$
-467246796	$12*(3-4/5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89$	-570715064	$1+234-(5+6)^*7^8*9$
-467250036	$-12*(3+4/5^{\wedge}6-7)^*89$	-570715066	$-1+234-(5+6)^*7^8*9$
-469763263	$1/2*(3^4*5^6-7/8^{\wedge}9)$	-570715532	$1-234-(5+6)^*7^8*9$
-470676417	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5-6^7)-8^{\wedge}9)$	-570715534	$-1-234-(5+6)^*7^8*9$
-470678847	$(-1-2)*(3^4*(5+6^7)+8^{\wedge}9)$	-570733821	$(1-(2+(3+4)^{-5})^6)^*7^8*9$
-474609348	$(-1-2)*(3^4/5^{\wedge}6(6-7-8)-9)$	-571996366	$(1+(2+3^4*(5+6))^*7^8)/-9$
-474609402	$(-1-2)*(3^4/5^{\wedge}6(6-7-8)+9)$	-573935607	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6-7^8))^*9$
-474876672	$(-1-2)*((3^4+5)^6*7^8+8^{\wedge}9)$	-573935625	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6-7^8))^*-9$
-492890485	$1/2-3*(4-5/6)^*7^8*9$	-575447031	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6-7-8))^*9$
-492890486	$1/-2-3*(4-5/6)^*7^8*9$	-575447049	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6-7-8))^*-9$
-495772241	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4))*(5-6^*7^8/9)$	-575963127	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6+7-8))^*9$
-495772757	$(-1-2/(3/4/5))^*(6^*7^8-9)$	-575963145	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6+7-8))^*-9$
-495773015	$(-1-2/(3/4/5))^*(6^*7^8+9)$	-575967735	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6-7/8))^*9$
-495773531	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))*(5+6^*7^8/9)$	-575967753	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6-7/8))^*-9$
-498078900	$-12*(3+4/5*(6+7^8*9))$	-576032247	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6+7/8))^*9$
-503095533	$(-1-2)*(3^{\wedge}(4^5-6))^*7+8^{\wedge}9$	-576032265	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6+7/8))^*-9$
-510603237	$(-1-2)*((3^4-5)^6*7^8-9)$	-576036855	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6-7+8))^*9$
-510603291	$(-1-2)*((3^4-5)^6*7^8+9)$	-576036873	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6-7+8))^*-9$
-511608825	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^4)*((5^6-7)^*8-9)$	-576552951	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6+7+8))^*9$
-511682535	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^4)*((5^6-7)^*8+9)$	-576552969	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6+7+8))^*-9$
-511858695	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^4))*((5^6-7)^*8+9)$	-577787877	$(-1-2)*((3^4+5)^6*7^8-9)$
-511932441	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^4))*((5^6-7)^*8-9)$	-577787931	$(-1-2)*((3^4+5)^6*7^8+9)$
-512067465	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^4)*((5^6+7)^*8-9)$	-578064375	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6+7^8))^*9$
-512141175	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^4)*((5^6+7)^*8+9)$	-578064393	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^4*(5^6+7^8))^*-9$
-512317559	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^4))*((5^6+7)^*8+9)$	-579362500	$1/2-(3^4-5/6)^*7^8*9$
-512391305	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3^4))*((5^6+7)^*8-9)$	-579362501	$1/-2-(3^4-5/6)^*7^8*9$
-516552228	$-12*(3^{\wedge}(4^5-6)-78)^*9$	-591468651	$(1+2)*(3+4/5)*(-6-7^8*9)$
-518831963	$-1+2*(34+5*(6-7^8*9))$	-599757294	$(-1-2)*((3+4^5)^6+7^8*9)$
-518832217	$1-2*(34+5*(6+7^8*9))$	-602653941	$(1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4^5-6))^*7-8)^*9$
-518832486	$12*(3-(4+5/6/7^8-8)^*9)$	-602654247	$(-1-2*(3^{\wedge}(4^5-6))^*7+8)^*9$
-524591977	$(-1+2^{\wedge}(3^4))/(5/(6-7^8/9))$	-607499991	$(1-2/3^4*(5^6)^7/8)^*9$
-524601805	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^4)/(5/(6+7^8/9))$	-607500009	$(-1-2/3^4*(5^6)^7/8)^*9$
-526500036	$-12*(3+4/5^{\wedge}6-7^8*9)$	-615189366	$(1-(2+3)^4*(5^6*7-8))^*9$
-529475129	$(1-2*3^4*5)^{\wedge}(6*(7-8)+9)$	-615189384	$(1+(2+3)^4*(5^6*7-8))^*-9$
-531727659	$1+2*(34^5-6^*7^8*9)$	-615279366	$(1-(2+3)^4*(5^6*7+8))^*9$
-531727661	$-1+2*(34^5-6^*7^8*9)$	-615279384	$(1+(2+3)^4*(5^6*7+8))^*-9$
-533411731	$(-1-2*3^4*5)^{\wedge}(6*(7-8)+9)$	-615848472	$12*(3+(4/5^{\wedge}6-7^8)^*9)$
-536433388	$1+23+4*(5^6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-615848544	$12*(-3+(4^5^6-7^8)^*9)$
-536433389	$1*23+4*(5^6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-619139699	$(12-3/45)*(-6-7^8*9)$
-536433390	$-1+23+4*(5^6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-621785905	$(1-2/3^{\wedge}(-4^5+6))^*(7^8+9)$
-536433397	$12+3+4*(5^6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-621786035	$(1+2/3^{\wedge}(-4^5+6))^*(7-8^*9)$
-536433427	$-12-3+4*(5^6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-622108620	$12*(3^4*5^6-7^8)^*9$
-536433434	$1-23+4*(5^6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-622544076	$12*3^4*(56-7^8/9)$
-536433435	$1*-23+4*(5^6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-622591209	$(1+2*(3^4*5-6/7^8-8))^*9$
-536433436	$-1-23+4*(5^6*7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-622591227	$(-1+2*(3^4*5-6/7^8-8))^*9$
-537308388	$1+23-4*(5^6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-622593804	$12*((3+4)^5*6-7^8*9)$
-537308389	$1*23-4*(5^6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-622595052	$12*((3+4)^5*6-7^8*9)$
-537308390	$-1+23-4*(5^6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-622595232	$12*(3+4^5*6-7^8*9)$
-537308397	$12+3-4*(5^6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-622595304	$-12*(3-4^5*6+7^8*9)$
-537308427	$-12-3-4*(5^6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-622595484	$-12*((3-4)^5*6+7^8*9)$
-537308434	$1-23-4*(5^6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-622596636	$-12*(3*(4-5)^6+7^8*9)$
-537308435	$1*-23-4*(5^6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-622596864	$12*(3^4+56-7^8*9)$
-537308436	$-1-23-4*(5^6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-622597845	$12*(-3/4+56-7^8*9)$
-544185837	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5-6^7)^*8+9)$	-622599171	$12*(3/4-56-7^8*9)$
-544185891	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5-6^7)^*8-9)$	-622600152	$-12*(3^4+56+7^8*9)$
-544194342	$(1+2)*(3^4*(5-6^7*8)+9)$	-622600380	$12*(3*(4-56)-7^8*9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-622601532	$12^*((3-45)^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-778248009	$(1+2)^*(3^*4+5^*(6-7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
-622601712	$12^*(3-45^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-778248021	$12+3^*(4+5^*(6-7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
-622601784	$-12^*(3+45^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-778248069	$-12-3^*(4-5^*(6-7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
-622601964	$-12^*((3+45)^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-778248201	$12+3^*(4-5^*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
-622603212	$-12^*((3+4)^*56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-778248249	$-12-3^*(4+5^*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
-622605789	$(1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6/7^{\wedge}8-8))^*9$	-778248261	$(1+2)^*(3^*-4-5^*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
-622605807	$(-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6/7^{\wedge}8-8))^*9$	-778248468	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9))$
-622652940	$12^*3^{\wedge}4^*(-56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-778248720	$(-12-3)^*(45-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-623088396	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*56+7^{\wedge}8)^*9$	-778248900	$(-12-3)^*(45+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-626057461	$(12/(2+3)+4)^*(-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-778251495	$(-12-3)^*(4^*56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-629348472	$12^*(3-(4^*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	-782936787	$1/2-(3+4)^*5/(6/(7+8^{\wedge}9))$
-629348544	$-12^*(3+(4^*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	-782936788	$-1/2-(3+4)^*5/(6/(7+8^{\wedge}9))$
-634122170	$(-1+23)^*45^*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-789776492	$12-(3^{\wedge}4+56)^*(7^{\wedge}8-9)$
-634134050	$(1-23)^*45^*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-789776516	$12-(3^{\wedge}4+56)^*(7^{\wedge}8-9)$
-637006279	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^*6^{\wedge}7-8))/9$	-789778958	$12-(3^{\wedge}4+56)^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-637013561	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^*6^{\wedge}7+8))/9$	-789778982	$-12-(3^{\wedge}4+56)^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-637806208	$-12^{\wedge}(3+4)/(5/(6^{\wedge}7+89))$	-794738287	$(1-(2^*3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$
-644245061	$-1/(2+3)+4/(5/6)^*(7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-794738321	$(1+(2^*3^{\wedge}4+5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(-8-9)$
-645988352	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3^*4)^*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*-8^{\wedge}9$	-809999784	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}-4^*(5^*6)^{\wedge}7-8^*9)$
-646447104	$(1+2^{\wedge}(-3^*4)^*(5^{\wedge}6+7))^*-8^{\wedge}9$	-809999949	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}-4^*(5^*6)^{\wedge}7-8-9)$
-648991505	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-809999997	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}-4^*(5^*6)^{\wedge}7+8-9)$
-648991507	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-810000003	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}-4^*(5^*6)^{\wedge}7+8+9)$
-650139823	$(1+2/3+4)^*((5+6)^{\wedge}7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-810000051	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}-4^*(5^*6)^{\wedge}7+8+9)$
-662945904	$1+23^*45^*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-810000216	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}-4^*(5^*6)^{\wedge}7+8^*9)$
-662945905	$1^*23^*45^*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-811182463	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4^*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-662945906	$-1+23^*45^*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-850885956	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)/5)^*6^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-662958324	$1-23^*45^*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-879710006	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)/(5/6))^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-662958325	$-1^*23^*45^*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-882013601	$1/2^*34^*(56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-662958326	$-1-23^*45^*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-882015505	$-1/2^*34^*(56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-665834515	$1/2-(3^*4+5/6)^*7^{\wedge}8^*9$	-888888889	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5^{\wedge}(-6+7+8))/9$
-665834516	$1/-2-(3^*4+5/6)^*7^{\wedge}8^*9$	-891239626	$(-1-2^{\wedge}(3+4)/(5/6))^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-688746519	$(1-2^*(3^{\wedge}(4^*5-6)-7)^*8)^*9$	-899307785	$1+234^*(5-6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-688746537	$(-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}(4^*5-6)-7)^*8)^*9$	-899307786	$1^*234^*(5-6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-688748535	$(1-2^*(3^{\wedge}(4^*5-6)+7)^*8)^*9$	-899307787	$-1+234^*(5-6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-688748553	$(-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}(4^*5-6)+7)^*8)^*9$	-899310125	$1-234^*(5+6^*7^{\wedge}8/9)$
-691769640	$(1+23)^*45^*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-920063676	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4)/5)^*-6^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-691782600	$(1+23)^*45^*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-933151266	$(1+2)^*((3^*4)^{\wedge}5-6/7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-698844915	$(-1-2/3)/((4+5)^{\wedge}-6/789)$	-933838713	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-704642568	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3+4^*5)/6)^*7^*8^*9$	-933847341	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^{\wedge}5-6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-704643576	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4^*5)/6)^*7^*8^*-9$	-933888546	$(1+2)^*(3/4^{\wedge}-5-6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-713469355	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5+6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-933888671	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(56-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-716416857	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7/8-9)$	-933888673	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(56-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-716486823	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(-6^{\wedge}7/8+9)$	-933888707	$1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(56-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-716785479	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7/8+9)$	-933888709	$-1+2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(56-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-716855481	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(-6^{\wedge}7/8-9)$	-933894678	$12+3^*(4^{\wedge}5-6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-723354607	$(1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$	-933894702	$-12+3^*(4^{\wedge}5-6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-723354641	$(-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$	-933896754	$(-1+23-4)^*(56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-731649627	$(-1-2)^*(3/(4^*5)^{\wedge}-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-933897504	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4+5-6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-736740792	$(1-(2-3^{\wedge}4/5)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-933897534	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4+5-6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-736740810	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4/5)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8))^*-9$	-933897657	$(1+2)^*((3+4)^*5-6/7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-742775424	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5^*6^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-933897867	$(-1-2)^*((3+4)^*5+6/7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-743659243	$(1+2/(3/4/5))^*(6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-933897990	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4+5+6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-743659415	$(-1-2/(3/4/5))^*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-933898020	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4+5+6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-747149167	$(1-(2^*3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(8+9)$	-933898770	$(1-23+4)^*(56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-747149201	$(1+(2^*3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*(-8-9)$	-933900822	$12-3^*(4^{\wedge}5+6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-752306530	$1/2-3^*(4+5/6)^*7^{\wedge}8^*9$	-933906815	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(56+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-752306531	$-1/2-3^*(4+5/6)^*7^{\wedge}8^*9$	-933906817	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(56+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-755709023	$(1-2/3^{\wedge}(-4^*5+6))^*(7+8^*9)$	-933906851	$1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(56+7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-755709181	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}(4^*5-6))^*(7+8^*9)$	-933906853	$-1-2^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(56+7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-755846208	$-12^{\wedge}3^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7-89)$	-933906978	$(1+2)^*(3^*-4^*5-6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-756153792	$-12^{\wedge}3^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7+89)$	-933948183	$(-1-2)^*((3+4)^{\wedge}5+6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-761186917	$(1+2/3+4)^*(5^{\wedge}6^*-7-8^{\wedge}9)$	-933956811	$(1+2)^*(-3^{\wedge}(4+5)-6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-762939453	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}(4^*5-6))/(7-8+9)$	-934644258	$(-1-2)^*((3^*4)^{\wedge}5+6/7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-767871582	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4)/5)^*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-9346461596	$(-1+2^{\wedge}3)^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6^*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-770929957	$(1+2^*3^{\wedge}4^*(5-6^{\wedge}7))^*(8+9)$	-938758443	$(1+2^*3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-770929991	$(-1+2^*3^{\wedge}4^*(5-6^{\wedge}7))^*(8+9)$	-938758499	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7+8^{\wedge}9)$
-770957497	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6^{\wedge}7))^*(8+9)$	-939519548	$12+3^{\wedge}4^*56-7^*8^{\wedge}9$
-770957531	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6^{\wedge}7))^*(8+9)$	-939519572	$-12+3^{\wedge}4^*56-7^*8^{\wedge}9$
-778244775	$(12+3)^*(4^*56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-939528620	$12-3^{\wedge}4^*56-7^*8^{\wedge}9$
-778247370	$(12+3)^*(45+6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-939528644	$-12-3^{\wedge}4^*56-7^*8^{\wedge}9$
-778247550	$(12+3)^*(45-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-940289693	$(1+2^*3)^*(4-5^{\wedge}6^*7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-778247802	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4+5^*(6-7^{\wedge}8^*9))$	-940289749	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4+5^{\wedge}6^*7+8^{\wedge}9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-942586596	$(1-2^{\wedge}3)^*(4*5^{\wedge}6*7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-1138346605	$(1-2/3^{\wedge}(-4*5+6)*7)^*(8+9)$
-944273412	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4/5)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-1138346639	$(-1-2*3^{\wedge}(4*5-6)*7)^*(8+9)$
-944273430	$(-1+(2+3^{\wedge}4/5)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8))^*9$	-1141425670	$(1-23)^*(-4*56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-945074417	$-1/2*((3+4)^*5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1141429278	$(1-23)^*(-4-56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-954468224	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*6^{\wedge}(7+8-9)$	-1141429454	$(1-23)^*(4-56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-955561536	$(-1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*5)^*6^{\wedge}(7+8-9)$	-1141429476	$(1-23)^*(-45-6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-959728770	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)-9)$	-1141429740	$(1-23)^*(-45+6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-959802480	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*(7+8)+9)$	-1141431456	$(1-23)^*(45-6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-960197502	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3*4))^*(5^{\wedge}6*(-7-8)+9)$	-1141431720	$(1-23)^*(45+6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-960271248	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3*4))^*(5^{\wedge}6*(-7-8)-9)$	-1141431742	$(1-23)^*(-4+56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-985779906	$1+(23-4)^*(56-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1141431918	$(1-23)^*(4+56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-985779908	$-1+(23-4)^*(56-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1141435526	$(1-23)^*(4*56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-985782034	$1-(23-4)^*(56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1155266421	$(-1-2*3^{\wedge}4/5)^*(6*7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-985782036	$-1-(23-4)^*(56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1162259888	$1-2*((3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5/6-789)$
-1006611840	$(-1-2)^*((3*(4+5))^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1162260252	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*5+(6-7-8)^{\wedge}9)$
-1015298847	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-8))^*9$	-1162260677	$1-2*(3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5/6+789$
-1015298865	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-8))^*9$	-1162262255	$1-2*(3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5/6-789$
-1015356879	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8))^*9$	-1162262682	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4*-5+(6-7-8)^{\wedge}9)$
-1015356897	$(-1+(2-3^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8))^*9$	-1162263044	$1-2*((3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5/6+789)$
-1017252604	$(1-(2+3)^{\wedge}(4*5-6))/(7+8-9)$	-1162263045	$-1*2*((3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5/6+789)$
-1025376255	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-8))^*9$	-1162263046	$-1-2*((3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5/6+789)$
-1025376273	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7-8))^*9$	-1167372336	$1/(2/(3-45*(6+7^{\wedge}8*9)))$
-1025434863	$(1-(2+3^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8))^*9$	-1169230140	$(1+2/3)^*(-4*(5+6)^{\wedge}7+8)^*9$
-1025434881	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4*5)^*(6^{\wedge}7+8))^*9$	-1181090663	$1+23*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1033121277	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}(4*(5+6-7))^*8-9)$	-1181090665	$-1+23*((4+5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1033121331	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}(4*(5+6-7))^*8+9)$	-1184616252	$-12*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*78-9)$
-1037654460	$12*3*45*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1184633748	$-12*3^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6*78+9)$
-1037664057	$(-1+2)*3+4*5*(6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1190079339	$1+23*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-1037664063	$1^{\wedge}2*-3+4*5*(6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1190079341	$-1+23*(4+(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-1037664297	$(-1+2)*3-4*5*(6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1190079523	$1-23*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-1037664303	$1^{\wedge}2*-3-4*5*(6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1190079525	$-1-23*(4-(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$
-1037673900	$12*3*-45*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1191876306	$1+23*(4*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1058828751	$(-1-2^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}(4+5-6))^*(7+8/9)$	-1191876308	$-1+23*(4*5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1078007689	$(12^{\wedge}3-45)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1192954339	$1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1078027885	$(12^{\wedge}3-45)^*(-6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1192954341	$-1+23*(4+5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1085880223	$1-2*((34-5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1192954523	$1-23*(4-5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1085880225	$-1-2*((34-5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1192954525	$-1-23*(4-5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1086088791	$(-1-2*3^{\wedge}4/5)^*(6*7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-1193172494	$1+23*(4^{\wedge}5*6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1087512559	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*(8+9)$	-1193172496	$-1+23*(4^{\wedge}5*6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1087512593	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6-7))^*(-8-9)$	-1193290116	$1+23*(4^{\wedge}5+6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1088487407	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7))^*(8+9)$	-1193290118	$-1+23*(4^{\wedge}5+6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1088487441	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4*(5^{\wedge}6+7))^*(-8-9)$	-1193290392	$1+23*(4^{\wedge}5-6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1096844814	$1+23*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1193290394	$-1+23*(4^{\wedge}5-6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1096844816	$-1+23*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8*9)$	-1193307596	$1+23*(45*6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1106375232	$12^{\wedge}3*(45*6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193307598	$-1+23*(45*6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1106454720	$12^{\wedge}3*(4*56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193308654	$1+23*(4*56-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1106738112	$12^{\wedge}3*(4+56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193308656	$-1+23*(4*56-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1106751936	$-12^{\wedge}3*(4-56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193312426	$1+23*(4+56-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1106753664	$12^{\wedge}3*(45+6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193312427	$1*23*(4+56-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1106774400	$12^{\wedge}3*(45-6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193312428	$-1+23*(4+56-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1106828832	$12^{\wedge}3*(45/6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193312610	$1-23*(4-56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1106854752	$-12^{\wedge}3*(45/6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193312611	$-1*23*(4-56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1106909184	$-12^{\wedge}3*(45-6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193312612	$-1-23*(4-56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1106929920	$-12^{\wedge}3*(45+6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193312633	$1+23*(45+6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1106931648	$12^{\wedge}3*(4-56-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193312634	$1*23*(45+6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1106945472	$-12^{\wedge}3*(4+56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193312635	$-1+23*(45+6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1107228864	$-12^{\wedge}3*(4*56+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193312794	$1+23*(4*(5+6)-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1107308352	$-12^{\wedge}3*(45*6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193312909	$1+23*(45-6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1114914254	$(1-2/(3^{\wedge}4-5/6))^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-1193312910	$1*23*(45-6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1124134088	$1-234*(5/6/7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-1193312911	$-1+23*(45-6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1124134089	$1*234*(5/6/7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-1193313484	$1+23*(4*5-6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1124134090	$-1-234*(5/6/7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-1193313783	$1+23*((4-5)^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1124138300	$1-234*(5/6/7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-1193314703	$1-23*(45-6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1124138301	$1*-234*(5/6/7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-1193314704	$-1*23*(45-6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1124138302	$-1-234*(5/6/7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-1193314705	$-1-23*(45-6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1126443874	$(-1-2/(3^{\wedge}4-5/6))^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-1193314979	$1-23*(45+6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1133113345	$(1-(2*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7*8-9)$	-1193314980	$-1*23*(45+6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1133136655	$(1-(2*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7*8+9)$	-1193314981	$-1-23*(45+6+7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1134863327	$(1+(2*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7*-8+9)$	-1193315002	$1+23*(4-56-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1134886673	$(1+(2*3)^{\wedge}4)^*(5^{\wedge}6*7*-8-9)$	-1193315003	$1*23*(4-56-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1135655159	$(12^{\wedge}3+45)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193315004	$-1+23*(4-56-7^{\wedge}8*9)$
-1135676435	$(12^{\wedge}3+45)^*(-6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1193315186	$1-23*(4+56+7^{\wedge}8*9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1193315187	$-1 \cdot 23^*(4+56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1323021830	$-1/2+(3/4-5)^*6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9$
-1193315188	$-1-23^*(4+56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1348961978	$(-1+23+4)^*(56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1193318958	$1-23^*(4^*56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1348964890	$(1-23-4)^*(56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1193318960	$-1-23^*(4^*56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1358809344	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4^*5)^*6^{\wedge}(7-8+9)$
-1193320016	$1-23^*(45^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1360487892	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5^*6^{\wedge}7-89)$
-1193320018	$-1-23^*(45^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1360490028	$-12^*(3^{\wedge}4^*5^*6^{\wedge}7+89)$
-1193337220	$1-23^*(4^{\wedge}5-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1362168576	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4^*5)^*6^{\wedge}(7-8+9)$
-1193337222	$-1-23^*(4^{\wedge}5-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1373290924	$1/2+(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}(6+7))/8^*9$
-1193337496	$1-23^*(4^{\wedge}5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1373290925	$1/-2+(3^{\wedge}4-5^{\wedge}(6+7))/8^*9$
-1193337498	$-1-23^*(4^{\wedge}5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1380093519	$(1+2^{\wedge}(3+4))/5^*(-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1193455118	$1-23^*(4^{\wedge}5^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1383552213	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5-6)^*7^{\wedge}8-9)$
-1193455120	$-1-23^*(4^{\wedge}5^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1383552267	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5-6)^*7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-1193673089	$1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1397049741	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-1193673091	$-1+23^*(4-5^{\wedge}6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1397049795	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-1193673273	$1-23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1400834331	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3^*(456-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1193673275	$-1-23^*(4+5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1400839326	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^*6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-1194751306	$1-23^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1400839380	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^*6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-1194751308	$-1-23^*(4^*5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1400843403	$(1+2)^{\wedge}3^*(4^*5^*6^{\wedge}7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1196548089	$1+23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	-1400843943	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-1196548090	$1^*23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	-1400843997	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5+6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-1196548091	$-1+23^*(4-(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	-1400845130	$1+(23+4)^*(56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1196548273	$1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	-1400845131	$(1^*23+4)^*(56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1196548274	$-1^*23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	-1400845132	$-1+(23+4)^*(56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1196548275	$-1-23^*(4+(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)^*9)$	-1400846373	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(-5+6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-1205536949	$1-23^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1400846427	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(-5+6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-1205536951	$-1-23^*((4+5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1400846859	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5-6+7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-1210608183	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4-5-6)^*7^{\wedge}8-9)$	-1400846913	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5-6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-1210608237	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4-5-6)^*7^{\wedge}8+9)$	-1400848154	$1-(23+4)^*(56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1212653184	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4-4^*(5^*6)^{\wedge}7+8^{\wedge}9)$	-1400848155	$(-1^*23-4)^*(56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1245191640	$(1+23)^*(4^*56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1400848156	$-1-(23+4)^*(56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1245195576	$(1+23)^*(4+56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1400849289	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(-5-6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-1245195768	$(-1-23)^*(4-56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1400849343	$(1+2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(-5-6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-1245196080	$(1+23)^*(45-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1400849883	$(-1-2)^{\wedge}3^*(4^*5^*6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1245197952	$(-1-23)^*(45-6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1400853906	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^*6+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-1245198264	$(1+23)^*(4-56-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1400853960	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^*6+7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-1245198456	$(-1-23)^*(4+56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1400858955	$(-1-2)^{\wedge}3^*(456+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1245202392	$(-1-23)^*(4^*56+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1404643491	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-1253675290	$1-((2^*3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5+67)/89$	-1404643545	$(-1-2)^*(3^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-1253675292	$-1-((2^*3^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}5+67)/89$	-1418141019	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4-5+6)^*7^{\wedge}8-9)$
-1275656679	$(1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7-8))^*9$	-1418141073	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4-5+6)^*7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-1275656697	$(1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7-8))^*-9$	-1457346807	$(1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6-7^*8))^*9$
-1275843303	$(1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+8))^*9$	-1457346825	$(1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6-7^*8))^*-9$
-1275843321	$(1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6^*7+8))^*-9$	-1458653175	$(1-(2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7^*8))^*9$
-1276327089	$(1-2^{\wedge}(3+4))/5^*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1458653193	$(1+(2^*3)^{\wedge}4^*(5^{\wedge}6+7^*8))^*-9$
-1289760759	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*(5-6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$	-1470024085	$(1+2/3+4)^*5^*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1289760777	$(-1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*(5-6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$	-1470024425	$(1+2/3+4)^*-5^*(6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$
-1289782798	$1-23^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1480781249	$1-2/((3/45)^{\wedge}6/(7^*8+9))$
-1289782800	$-1-23^*(4^{\wedge}(5+6)+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1480781251	$-1-2/((3/45)^{\wedge}6/(7^*8+9))$
-1290129399	$(1-(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*(5+6^{\wedge}7/8))^*9$	-1487317083	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-1290129417	$(1+(2^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}4^*(5+6^{\wedge}7/8))^*-9$	-1487317137	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-1293413059	$1-2^*((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1487320179	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$
-1293413061	$-1-2^*((34-5)^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1487320233	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$
-1297079475	$(1+2^*3^*4)^*(5^*6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1530081951	$(1+2)^*(3+4/5)^*(6+7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-1297079950	$(1+2^*3^*4)^*(5+6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1530082578	$(1+2)^*(3+4/5)^*(6^*-7-8^{\wedge}9)$
-1297080117	$(12-(3^{\wedge}4-56)^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1531809639	$(1+(2-(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$
-1297080200	$(1+2^*3^*4)^*(-5+6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1531809657	$(-1+(2-(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$
-1297080213	$12-(3^{\wedge}4-56)^*7^{\wedge}8^*9$	-1531809927	$(1-(2+(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*9$
-1297080237	$-12-(3^{\wedge}4-56)^*7^{\wedge}8^*9$	-1531809945	$(1+(2+(3^{\wedge}4-5)^*6^{\wedge}7)^*8)^*-9$
-1297080250	$(1+2^*3^*4)^*(5-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1555215203	$(1+(2-3^{\wedge}4^*5^*6)^*7^{\wedge}8)/9$
-1297080333	$(12+(3^{\wedge}4-56)^*7^{\wedge}8^*9)^*-9$	-1557777337	$(1+(2+3^{\wedge}4^*5^*6)^*7^{\wedge}8)/-9$
-1297080500	$(-1-2^*3^*4)^*(5+6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1571906249	$1-2/((3/45)^{\wedge}6/(78-9))$
-1297080975	$(1+2^*3^*4)^*(5^*-6-7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1571906250	$-1^*2/((3/45)^{\wedge}6/(78-9))$
-1307544123	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}(4^*5)+6-7)/8-9)$	-1571906251	$-1-2/((3/45)^{\wedge}6/(78-9))$
-1307544177	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}(4^*5)+6-7)/8+9)$	-1579555455	$1-2^*((3^{\wedge}4+56)^*7^{\wedge}8-9)$
-1308597569	$(-1-2^*(3-4^{\wedge}5))^*(6-7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1579555457	$1-2^*((3^{\wedge}4+56)^*7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-1308622085	$(-1+2^*(3-4^{\wedge}5))^*(6+7^{\wedge}8/9)$	-1579555491	$1-2^*((3^{\wedge}4+56)^*7^{\wedge}8-9)$
-1314373233	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$	-1579555493	$-1-2^*((3^{\wedge}4+56)^*7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-1314373287	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$	-1580078125	$(1-2^*3^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6+7-8)^{\wedge}9$
-1314375969	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(-6-7^{\wedge}8)+9)$	-1583984375	$(-1-2^*3^{\wedge}4^*5)^*(6+7-8)^{\wedge}9$
-1314376023	$(1+2)^*((3^{\wedge}4-5)^*(-6-7^{\wedge}8)-9)$	-1584169788	$(1-234/5)^*6^*(7^{\wedge}8+9)$
-1317911094	$(-1-2)^*((3^*(4+5))^{\wedge}6+7^{\wedge}8^*9)$	-1591085049	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5+6)^*7^{\wedge}8-9)$
-1323021829	$1/2+(3/4-5)^*6^*7^{\wedge}8^*9$	-1591085103	$(-1-2)^*((3^{\wedge}4+5+6)^*7^{\wedge}8+9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1598046875	$(1 - (2^3)^4/5)^*(6+7-8)^9$	-1815912133	$(1-2^3)^*(4-5*(6-7^8*9))$
-1601953125	$(1+(2^3)^4/5)^*(-6-7+8)^9$	-1815912497	$(-1+2^3)^*(4-5*(6+7^8*9))$
-1610231712	$12^*(3^4*5^6*7-8^9)$	-1815912553	$(1-2^3)^*(4+5*(6+7^8*9))$
-1610287116	$12^*(3^4*5^6*7-8^9)$	-1815914275	$(1-2-34)^*(56+7^8*9)$
-1610542752	$12^*(3^4*(5+67)-8^9)$	-1816217469	$(-1-2/3^4-4*5)^*(6^7*8-9)$
-1610543592	$12^*((3^4+5)^6*7-8^9)$	-1816232067	$(-1-2/3^4-4*5)^*(6^7*8+9)$
-1610551632	$12^*((3^4-5)^6*7-8^9)$	-1823324202	$12^*(-3+4/56)^*7^8*9$
-1610552472	$-12^*(3^4*(5-67)+8^9)$	-1862993088	$12^3*(4-5^6*(78-9))$
-1610558220	$12^*(3^4*56+7-8^9)$	-1863006912	$-12^3*(4+5^6*(78-9))$
-1610558388	$12^*(3^4*56-7-8^9)$	-1867793364	$12^3*(4+56-7^8*9)$
-1610601228	$12^*((3^4+56)^7-8^9)$	-1867793507	$1+(2+34)^*(56-7^8*9)$
-1610607072	$12^*(3^4*5+67-8^9)$	-1867793509	$-1+(2+34)^*(56-7^8*9)$
-1610608680	$12^*(3^4*5-67-8^9)$	-1867793652	$-12^3*(4-56+7^8*9)$
-1610610636	$12^*(3^4*56-7-8^9)$	-1867794120	$12^3*(45-6-7^8*9)$
-1610614836	$-12^*((3^4-56)^7+8^9)$	-1867796928	$-12^3*(45-6+7^8*9)$
-1610616792	$-12^*(3^4*5-67+8^9)$	-1867797396	$12^3*(4-56-7^8*9)$
-1610618400	$-12^*(3^4*5+67+8^9)$	-1867797539	$1-(2+34)^*(56+7^8*9)$
-1610624244	$-12^*((3^4+56)^7+8^9)$	-1867797541	$-1-(2+34)^*(56+7^8*9)$
-1610667084	$-12^*(3^4*56-7+8^9)$	-1867797684	$-12^3*(4+56+7^8*9)$
-1610667252	$-12^*(3^4*56+7+8^9)$	-1872857880	$12^3*(4-(5^6+7^8)^9)$
-1610673000	$12^*(3^4*(5-67)-8^9)$	-1872858168	$-12^3*(4+(5^6+7^8)^9)$
-1610673840	$-12^*((3^4-5)^6*7+8^9)$	-1879039119	$1+2^*(3^4*56-7^8*9)$
-1610681880	$-12^*((3^4+5)^6*7+8^9)$	-1879039121	$-1+2^*(3^4*56-7^8*9)$
-1610682720	$-12^*(3^4*(5+67)+8^9)$	-1879057263	$1-2^*(3^4*56+7^8*9)$
-1610938356	$-12^*(3^4*5^6*7+8^9)$	-1893486036	$(12-(3^4-5)^6*7)^8*9$
-1610993760	$-12^*(3^4*56*7+8^9)$	-1893487092	$12-(3^4-5)^6*7^8*9$
-1612993838	$(1-234/(5/6))^*(7^8+9)$	-1893487116	$-12-(3^4-5)^6*7^8*9$
-1624523458	$(-1-234/(5/6))^*(7^8+9)$	-1893488172	$(12+(3^4-5)^6*7)^8*9$
-1629132951	$(1-2*3^4/5)^*(6+7^8*9)$	-1908874320	$1-(2^3*4-5*(67-8))/9$
-1632557439	$(1+(2+3^4*(5-6^7))/8)^9$	-1908874322	$-1-(2^3*4-5*(67-8))/9$
-1632557457	$(-1+(2+3^4*(5-6^7))/8)^9$	-1908874347	$-1-(2^3*4+5-67-8)/9$
-1632557727	$(1-(2-3^4*(5-6^7))/8)^9$	-1912266846	$12^*(3+4/56)^*7^8*9$
-1632557745	$(1+(2-3^4*(5-6^7))/8)^9$	-1917841519	$(1+(2-3^4*5)^6*7)^8*(8+9)$
-1632586335	$12+3^4*(5-6^7*8^9)$	-1917841553	$(-1+(2-3^4*5)^6*7)^8*(8+9)$
-1632586359	$-12+3^4*(5-6^7*8^9)$	-1919676661	$(1+2+34)^*(56-7^8*9)$
-1632587145	$12-3^4*(5+6^7*8^9)$	-1919680805	$(1+2+34)^*(-56-7^8*9)$
-1632587169	$-12-3^4*(5+6^7*8^9)$	-1923787449	$(1+2/(3/4/5))^*(6-7-8^9)$
-1632615759	$(1+(2-3^4*(5+6^7))/8)^9$	-1923787621	$(-1-2/(3/4/5))^*(6+7+8^9)$
-1632615777	$(-1+(2-3^4*(5+6^7))/8)^9$	-1936877167	$(1-(2+3^4*5)^6*7)^8*(8+9)$
-1632616047	$(1-(2+3^4*(5+6^7))/8)^9$	-1936877201	$(1+(2+3^4*5)^6*7)^8*(-8-9)$
-1632616065	$(1+(2+3^4*(5+6^7))/8)^9$	-1971561906	$12^*(3-(4-5/6)^*(7^8*9))$
-1653347508	$(1+234/5)^6*(7^8+9)$	-1971561978	$-12^*(3+(4-5/6)^*(7^8*9))$
-1656876522	$(1+(2-3^4)^5)/(6/7-8+9)$	-1992315456	$-12^3/45*(6+7^8*9)$
-1670265054	$(1-(2^3*4-56)^7/8)/9$	-2008294908	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4-5)^*(-6+7+8^9)$
-1670639523	$(1-2*3^4)/(5/(6+7^8*9))$	-2018021511	$(12+3^4*(5-6^7))^8*9$
-1681014213	$(1+2*3^4/5*(6-7^8))^9$	-2018022567	$12+3^4*(5-6^7)^8*9$
-1681014231	$(-1+2*3^4/5*(6-7^8))^9$	-2018022591	$-12+3^4*(5-6^7)^8*9$
-1712145861	$(1+2)^*(3^4-(5+6)^7*8^9)$	-2018023647	$(-12+3^4*(5-6^7))^8*9$
-1712145933	$(1+2)^*(3^4-(5+6)^7*8^9)$	-2018058207	$12+3^4*(5-6^7*8^9)$
-1729440192	$-12^*((3^4-56)^7*8^9)$	-2018058231	$-12+3^4*(5-6^7*8^9)$
-1729440408	$-12^*((3^4-56)^7*8^9)$	-2018059017	$12-3^4*(5+6^7*8^9)$
-1732899381	$(-1-2*3^4/5)^*(6+7^8*9)$	-2018059041	$-12-3^4*(5+6^7*8^9)$
-1733363559	$(1+(2-(3^4+5)^6*7)^8)^9$	-2018093601	$(12-3^4*(5+6^7))^8*9$
-1733363577	$(-1+(2-(3^4+5)^6*7)^8)^9$	-2018094657	$12-3^4*(5+6^7)^8*9$
-1733363847	$(1-(2+(3^4+5)^6*7)^8)^9$	-2018094681	$-12-3^4*(5+6^7)^8*9$
-1733363865	$(1+(2+(3^4+5)^6*7)^8)^9$	-2018095737	$(12+3^4*(5+6^7))^8*9$
-1764027202	$1^2*3^4*(56-7^8*9)$	-2018236962	$(1+2)^*(3^4-4+5)^*(6-7-8^9)$
-1764028083	$1+2+3^4*(5*6-7^8*9)$	-2023443423	$12^3-(45-6)^7*8^9$
-1764029481	$1-2-3^4*(5+6+7^8*9)$	-2023446879	$-12^3-(45-6)^7*8^9$
-1764029482	$1^*-2-3^4*(5+6+7^8*9)$	-2040675111	$(1-2/3^4-4*5)^*(6^7*8-9)^9$
-1764029483	$-1-2-3^4*(5+6+7^8*9)$	-2040675129	$(-1-2/3^4-4*5)^*(6^7*8-9)^9$
-1764031010	$1^2*3^4*(56+7^8*9)$	-2040721767	$(1-2*3^4*(5/6^7-8))^9$
-1776937490	$1-2/((3/45)^6/78)+9$	-2040721785	$(-1-2*3^4*(5/6^7-8))^9$
-1776937492	$-1-2/((3/45)^6/78)+9$	-2040733287	$(1-2*(3^4*5/6^7-8))^9$
-1776937508	$1-2/((3/45)^6/78)-9$	-2040733305	$(-1-2*(3^4*5/6^7-8))^9$
-1776937510	$-1-2/((3/45)^6/78)-9$	-2040733575	$(1-2*(3^4*5/6^7-8))^9$
-1789970710	$1/2-(3/4+5)^6*7^8*9$	-2040733593	$(-1-2*(3^4*5/6^7-8))^9$
-1789970711	$1/-2-(3/4+5)^6*7^8*9$	-2040745095	$(1-2*3^4*(5/6^7-8))^9$
-1811738511	$(1-2/3^4-4*5)^*(6^7*8-9)$	-2040745113	$(-1-2*3^4*(5/6^7-8))^9$
-1811753073	$(1-2/3^4-4*5)^*(6^7*8+9)$	-2040791751	$(1-2/3^4-4*5)^*(6^7*8+9)^9$
-1815910355	$(1^2+34)^*(56-7^8*9)$	-2040791769	$(-1-2/3^4-4*5)^*(6^7*8+9)^9$
-1815912077	$(-1+2^3)^*(4+5*(6-7^8*9))$	-2075326120	$(12^3+4)^*(56-7^8*9)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2075330600	$(-12 \cdot 3 - 4) \cdot (56 + 7^8 \cdot 9)$		
-2101269964	$1/2 - 3^{(4+5)}/6 \cdot 7^8/9$		
-2101269965	$1/-2 - 3^{(4+5)}/6/7^8 - 8/9$		
-2105977536	$12^3 \cdot (4 - 5^6 \cdot 78 + 9)$		
-2105991360	$-12^3 \cdot (4 + 5^6 \cdot 78 - 9)$		
-2106008640	$12^3 \cdot (4 - 5^6 \cdot 78 - 9)$		
-2106022464	$-12^3 \cdot (4 + 5^6 \cdot 78 + 9)$		
-2142629076	$(12 - (3^4 + 5) \cdot 6^7) \cdot 89$		
-2142630132	$12 - (3^4 + 5) \cdot 6^7 \cdot 89$		
-2142630156	$-12 - (3^4 + 5) \cdot 6^7 \cdot 89$		
-2142631212	$(12 + (3^4 + 5) \cdot 6^7) \cdot -89$		

Supplement 4

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-30172	$-9+(8+7*(6-5^4)/3)*21$	-99474	$(-9-87*6)*(5^4/3-21)$
-35284	$9+87*((6-5^4/3)*2-1)$	-100446	$9*(87-6*5^4*3)+21$
-38101	$98*(7+6)-5^4*3*21$	-100853	$9*(8*7-6*(5^4*3+2))+1$
-38652	$9-(8-7*6+5^4*3)*21$	-100855	$9*(8*7-6*(5^4*3+2))-1$
-40080	$9+(8-7*6-5^4*3)*21$	-101334	$9*(-8*7/6+5^4*(3-21))$
-40667	$(9+8)*-76-5^4*3*21$	-101507	$(-9-8)*(76+5^4/3)*21$
-41786	$(9+8)*(7*6-5^4*(3+2-1))$	-101861	$-9*(8*7+6*(5^4*3+2))+1$
-47698	$98*(7-6^5*4/3/21)$	-102012	$-9*(87+6*5^4*3)+21$
-48809	$9*-8-(7+6)*(5^4*3*2-1)$	-104383	$9+8*(7+6-(5^4-3)*21)$
-49072	$-9*(8+7*(6/5/4)^{-3*21})$	-104480	$98+(7^4+5/4)*(3^4-2-1)$
-52177	$9*8-7*6*(5^4-3)*2-1$	-104609	$-9-8*(7+6+(5^4-3)*21)$
-52831	$-9*8-7*(6*(5^4+3)*2+1)$	-105140	$-98-7*(6+5^4*(3+21))$
-56698	$9+(8-(7+6)*5^4/3)*21$	-105391	$9+8*(7+6-(5^4+3)*21)$
-56777	$98-(7+6)*5^4/3*21$	-105536	$(9+8)*(7*6+5^4*(3^2+1))$
-57034	$9-(8+(7+6)*5^4/3)*21$	-105572	$9*8+7^4*(5/(4+3)^2-1)$
-60940	$(-9+8/7)/(6^5-4*(3+2))^{\wedge-1}$	-105716	$-9*8+7^4*(5/(4+3)^2-1)$
-61549	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)-5^4*(3+2-1)$	-106884	$-9*(8*7*6*5^4/32+1)$
-63332	$(9+8/7)*(6-5^4*(3^2+1))$	-106989	$(9*8+7*6)*(5^4*3/2-1)$
-63678	$9+((8/7-6)/5^4-4+3)*21$	-109698	$9-87*(6+(5^4+3)*2-1)$
-63804	$9+((8/7-6)/5^4-4-3)*21$	-113994	$9*(87*6-(5^4+3)*21)$
-64465	$(-9-8)*(7*6+5^4*3*2)-1$	-118700	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^4*3+2))+1$
-64473	$-9*(8-7*6)*(5^4*3+21)$	-118702	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^4*3+2))-1$
-64475	$9*8*(7*6-5^4*3/2)+1$	-118763	$-9*(8+7*6*(5^4+3)/2)+1$
-67312	$9*(8+7-(6*5^4-3)*2)-1$	-119211	$9*87-6*(5^4*32-1)$
-67404	$9+87+6*5^4*(3-21)$	-119415	$(9-8*(7+6))*(5^4+3)*2+1$
-67418	$9*(8+7-(6*5^4+3)*2)+1$	-119721	$-9-87*6*(5^4/3+21)$
-67420	$9*(8+7-(6*5^4+3)*2)-1$	-119980	$98/7-6*(5^4*32-1)$
-67436	$9*(8-7-(6*5^4-3)*2)+1$	-120599	$9-8*(76+5^4*(3+21))$
-67514	$-98/7+6*5^4*(3-21)$	-120617	$-9-8*(76+5^4*(3+21))$
-67562	$-9*(8-7+(6*5^4+3)*2)+1$	-120789	$-9*87-6*(5^4*32+1)$
-67564	$-9*(8-7+(6*5^4+3)*2)-1$	-121921	$-9-8*7/(6/(5^4-3))*21$
-67580	$-9*(8+7+(6*5^4-3)*2)+1$	-123827	$9*8-7^4*6-5^4*(3^2+1)$
-67596	$-9-87+6*5^4*(3-21)$	-125216	$(-98+7)*6*(5^4/3+21)$
-67814	$9*(8-7-6*(5^4+3)*2)+1$	-126897	$-9+(8-76)*(5^4-3)*(2+1)$
-68748	$(-9-8)*((7+6)*(5^4-3)/2+1)$	-127534	$(-9-8)*(7+(6*5^4-3)*2+1)$
-72509	$-9-87/6*5^4*(3^2-1)$	-127704	$(-9-8)*(7+(6*5^4+3)*2-1)$
-74696	$(9/8/(7^4*6*5/(4-3)+2))^{\wedge-1}$	-128208	$-9*(8+7*6*(5^4/3-21))$
-78358	$98/7-6*(5^4-3)*21$	-128937	$-9+(8-76)*(5^4*3+21)$
-79114	$98/7-6*(5^4+3)*21$	-129315	$9*(-8+7/6/5)*(43^2+1)$
-81348	$-98-(7+6)*5^4*(3^2+1)$	-130302	$9*(87*6-5^4*(3+21))$
-84112	$-98-7^4*6*5/(4+3)+21$	-130622	$98-(7^4*6-5+4)*(3^4-2+1)$
-84154	$-98-7^4*6*5/(4+3)-21$	-130648	$9*8-(7^4*6-5+4)*(3^4-2+1)$
-84810	$-9*(8+7/6)*(5+4^4(3+2)-1)$	-130792	$-9*8-(7^4*6-5+4)*(3^4-2+1)$
-86231	$9-8*7/6*5*(43^2-1)$	-130818	$-98-(7^4*6-5+4)*(3^4-2+1)$
-88068	$-9*((8+(7^4*6-5)/4)/3-21)$	-131993	$9*(8*(7*6-5^4*3)-2)+1$
-88114	$98-(7^4*6-5)/4*3+21$	-134081	$9*(8*(7+6-5^4*3)-2)+1$
-88310	$-98-(7^4*6-5)/4*3+21$	-134083	$9*(8*(7+6-5^4*3)-2)-1$
-88352	$-98-(7^4*6-5)/4*3-21$	-134899	$9*(8*(7/6-5^4*3)+2)-1$
-89248	$9-(8-7/6)*(5^4-3)*21$	-134933	$9*(8*(7/6-5^4*3)-2)+1$
-89477	$9*(8*(7-6*5^4/3)+2)+1$	-135053	$-9*(8*(7+6+5^4*3)-2)+1$
-89479	$9*(8*(7-6*5^4/3)+2)-1$	-135067	$-9*(8*(7/6+5^4*3)-2)-1$
-89513	$9*(8*(7-6*5^4/3)-2)+1$	-135089	$-9*(8*(7-6+5^4*3)+2)+1$
-89719	$98*((7*6-5^4*3)/2+1)$	-135101	$-9*(8*(7/6+5^4*3)+2)+1$
-89767	$9+8*(7-6*5^4*3+21)$	-135103	$-9*(8*(7/6+5^4*3)+2)-1$
-90109	$9-(8-7/6)*(5^4+3)*21$	-135917	$-9*(8*(7+6+5^4*3)-2)+1$
-90365	$9-87*6*(5^4/3/2-1)$	-135919	$-9*(8*(7+6+5^4*3)-2)-1$
-90485	$-9*(8*(7+6*5^4/3)-2)+1$	-135923	$(9-8*7*6)*(5^4/3*2-1)$
-90487	$-9*(8*(7+6*5^4/3)-2)-1$	-135953	$-9*(8*(7+6+5^4*3)+2)+1$
-90943	$9+8*(7-6*(5^4*3+21))$	-135955	$-9*(8*(7+6+5^4*3)+2)-1$
-91258	$-9-87*6*5^4/3/2+1$	-136566	$-9*(87-6)*(5^4/3-21)$
-91294	$98+7*(6-(5^4-3)*21)$	-136577	$(9-8*7*6)*(5^4/3*2+1)$
-91385	$98*(7-(6+5^4*3)/2+1)$	-137127	$9-8/7*6*(5^4*32-1)$
-91490	$-98+7*(6-(5^4-3)*21)$	-137702	$9*8+7*((6-5-4)^3+2+1)$
-92117	$9-87*6*(5^4/3/2+1)$	-138005	$9*(-8*(7*6+5^4*3)+2)+1$
-92135	$-9-87*6*(5^4/3/2+1)$	-138007	$9*(-8*(7*6+5^4*3)+2)-1$
-92372	$-98+7*(6-(5^4+3)*21)$	-138043	$-9*(8*(7*6+5^4*3)+2)-1$
-92456	$-98-7*(6+(5^4+3)*21)$	-138372	$-98-7^4*6-5^4*(32+1)$
-96926	$98-7^4*6+5^4*(32+1)$	-139853	$98+7*(6-5^4*32+1)$
-97779	$9-87*6*(5^4/3-21)$	-140352	$9*(8-76)*(5^4/3+21)$
-98176	$98-7^4*6+5^4*(32-1)$	-140493	$-9*8*(76+5^4*3)-21$
-98372	$-98-7^4*6+5^4*(32-1)$	-141051	$9*(8-76*(5^4/3-2)+1)$
-99138	$(9-87)*(6*5^4/3+21)$	-141195	$-9*(8+7*6*(5^4/3-2)-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-141213	$-9*(8+76*(5^4/3-2)+1)$	-182929	$9-876*(5^4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-141702	$(9*8+7*6)*((5^4-3)^*-2+1)$	-182947	$-9-876*(5^4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-141963	$(9/8-76)*(5^4*3+21)$	-183226	$(9-876)*(5^4/3+2+1)$
-142086	$9*(8-76*(5^4/3-2^{\wedge}-1))$	-183315	$(-9+8/7)*(6^{\wedge}5+4-3)*(2+1)$
-142230	$-9*(8+76*(5^4/3-2^{\wedge}-1))$	-183596	$(-98+7/6)*(5^4*3+21)$
-142239	$9*(8-76*5^4/3+21)$	-184242	$9-876*(5^4/3+2)+1$
-142617	$9*(8-76*5^4/3-21)$	-184243	$9-876*(5^4/3+2)/1$
-142770	$9*(8-76*(5^4/3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	-184244	$9-876*(5^4/3+2)-1$
-142817	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}(6-5+4)-3)/2-1)$	-184261	$-9-876*(5^4/3+2)/1$
-142841	$9-(8/7+6)*(5^4*32-1)$	-184262	$-9-876*(5^4/3+2)-1$
-142914	$-9*(8+76*(5^4/3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	-184485	$-98*(7+(6*5^4+3)/2-1)$
-143070	$(9*8+7*6)*((5^4+3)^*-2+1)$	-184805	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)/21)$
-143405	$(-9-8*7*6)*(5^4/3*2-1)$	-184949	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3)/21)$
-143787	$9*(8-76*(5^4/3+2)+1)$	-185119	$9-876*(5^4/3+2+1)$
-143931	$-9*(8+76*(5^4/3+2)-1)$	-185709	$-9*(8*7/6+5^4*(32+1))$
-144624	$-9*(8+76*(5^4/3+2+1))$	-186146	$(-9-876)*(5^4/3+2)-1$
-145475	$9*(8-(7+6)*(5^4-3)^*2)+1$	-187887	$-98*(7*6+5^4*3)-21$
-145477	$9*(8-(7+6)*(5^4-3)^*2)-1$	-188020	$(-98-7/6)*(5^4*3+21)$
-145558	$(-9*87+6)*(5^4/3-21)$	-189087	$9-8*(76*(5^4-3)/2+1)$
-145624	$(9/(8*(7+6)-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	-189089	$-9-8*(76*(5^4-3)/2-1)$
-145803	$(9-87)*(6+5^4*3)-21$	-189958	$(9+8)*(76+5^4*(3-21))$
-146630	$(-9-8*7/6)/((5*4)^{\wedge}3-2)^{\wedge}-1$	-189971	$9-8*((76*5^4-3)/2-1)$
-147806	$(-9*87-6)*(5^4/3-21)$	-190011	$9-8*((76*5^4+3)/2+1)$
-148997	$-9*((8+7*6*(5+4))/3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-190029	$-9-8*((76*5^4+3)/2+1)$
-153223	$-98*(7-6+5^4*(3/2+1))$	-190911	$9-8*(76*(5^4+3)/2+1)$
-154399	$-98*(7+6+5^4*(3/2+1))$	-190913	$-9-8*(76*(5^4+3)/2-1)$
-156573	$-9*(87*6+5^4*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-194811	$-9*(8*(7+6)*5^4/3-21)$
-159003	$9*((8+76)*(5^4/3-2)+1)$	-195992	$98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4/3-2-1)$
-159694	$9*(-8+7*6)-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	-195998	$98-(7^{\wedge}6*5+43)/(2+1)$
-160306	$9*(8-7*6)-(5*4)^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$	-196006	$98-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)/3-21$
-161293	$(-9+8-7*6)*(5^4*3*2+1)$	-196018	$9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4/3-2-1)$
-163750	$(9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)^*4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-196160	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)/3+21$
-163930	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)^*4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-196162	$-9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4/3-2-1)$
-166348	$-98-76*5^4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-196175	$-9*8-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3)/(2+1)$
-166685	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-196188	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4/3-2-1)$
-167634	$-9*(87*(6+5^4/3)-21)$	-196194	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6*5+43)/(2+1)$
-168426	$9-(8+7)*(6*5^4*3-21)$	-197175	$9-8*(7+6)*(5^4*3+21)$
-171192	$(-98+7)*(6+5^4*3)-21$	-197484	$(-98-7)*(6+5^4*3)+21$
-171673	$(-9/(8+(7-6/5^{\wedge}-4/3)^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	-198697	$(9-8*7-6)*(5^4*3*2-1)$
-174519	$9*(8*76-5^4*3*2+1)$	-198803	$(9-8*7-6)*(5^4*3*2+1)$
-176642	$9*(8*7+(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-198911	$9*87/(6/(5-43))^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-176644	$9*(8*7+(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-199815	$9*(8+7)*6-5^4*3*21$
-176767	$(9-8*7)*((6+5^4*3)^*2-1)$	-200382	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-5^4*3*21$
-176861	$(9-8*7)*((6+5^4*3)^*2+1)$	-200484	$9*(8+7)+6-5^4*3*21$
-177283	$9*(-8-7+(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-200496	$9*(8+7)-6-5^4*3*21$
-177602	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*((5/(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-200766	$-9*(8+7)-6-5^4*3*21$
-177746	$-9*8-7^{\wedge}6*((5/(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$	-201183	$-9*(8*7+6)-5^4*3*21$
-177785	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2)+1$	-201435	$9*(8+7)*6-5^4*3*21$
-177787	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))/2)-1$	-201561	$9*-8*(7+6)-5^4*3*21$
-178024	$(9-876)*(5^4/3-2-1)$	-201995	$9*(8*7-6*5^4*3*2)+1$
-178030	$(9-8*(7+6))*(5^4*3-2+1)$	-201997	$9*(8*7-6*5^4*3*2)-1$
-178192	$(-9*87+6)*(5^4/3+21)$	-202303	$9*(8+(7-6/5^{\wedge}-4*3)^*2)-1$
-178220	$(9-8*(7+6))*(5^4*3+2-1)$	-202697	$-9*(8+(7+6/5^{\wedge}-4*3)^*2)+1$
-178410	$(9-8*(7+6))*(5^4*3+2+1)$	-202699	$-9*(8+(7+6/5^{\wedge}-4*3)^*2)-1$
-178890	$(9-876)*(5^4/3-2)+1$	-203003	$-9*(8*7+6*5^4*3*2)+1$
-178891	$(9-876)*(5^4/3-2)*1$	-203005	$-9*(8*7+6*5^4*3*2)-1$
-178892	$(9-876)*(5^4/3-2)-1$	-203448	$9*8*7*((6-5^4/3)^*2+1)$
-179403	$(9+87)*(6-5^4*3)+21$	-203890	$(-9/(8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*(4+3)+2))^{\wedge}-1$
-179451	$9*(8*7+6-5^4*3*2-1)$	-203914	$(-9/(8+7*(6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-179863	$9-876*(5^4/3-2-1)$	-205718	$-9+(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4/3)^*21$
-179881	$-9-876*(5^4/3-2-1)$	-205767	$-9*(8/7*(6+5^4*3*2)-1)$
-180153	$9*(8*76-5^4*(32+1))$	-205779	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4/3*21$
-180555	$(-9-87)*(6+5^4*3)+21$	-205785	$-9*(8/7*(6+5^4*3*2)+1)$
-180597	$(-9-87)*(6+5^4*3)-21$	-205890	$(-9-8-7^{\wedge}(6+5-4))/(3+2-1)$
-180739	$9-876*(5^4/3-2)/1$	-205975	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4/3*21$
-180740	$9-876*(5^4/3-2)-1$	-206036	$9-(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4/3)^*21$
-180758	$-9-876*(5^4/3-2)-1$	-211832	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5-4/(3+2))+1$
-182359	$(9-876)*(5^4/3+2)*1$	-211834	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5-4/(3+2))-1$
-182360	$(9-876)*(5^4/3+2)-1$	-211840	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5-(4+2)^{\wedge}-1)$
-182408	$-98/(7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+43)^{\wedge}-2^{\wedge}1$	-212805	$-9*(8+76*(5^4-3)/2+1)$
-182605	$(-9-876)*(5^4/3-2)*1$	-213101	$98*(7+6-5^4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$
-182606	$(-9-876)*(5^4/3-2)-1$	-213636	$(9*8+7*6)*(5^4*-3+2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-213693	$(9*8+7*6)*(5^4*-3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-264450	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4)+321$
-213864	$(9*8+7*6)*(5^4*-3-2+1)$	-264948	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4)-321$
-214092	$(9*8+7*6)*(5^4*-3-2-1)$	-264987	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3+21)$
-214857	$-9*(8+76*(5^4+3)/2+1)$	-265068	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+32+1)$
-215771	$-9*8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-265092	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4)-321$
-216552	$9*8-7*((6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*2+1)$	-265338	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3*21)$
-218214	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5-43*21)$	-268633	$9*8*(7+(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*2)-1$
-219068	$9*(8-(7+6)*(5^4*3-2))+1$	-269805	$(9+8*(7-6/5^{\wedge}-4*3))*^*(2+1)$
-219070	$9*(8-(7+6)*(5^4*3-2))-1$	-269859	$(-9+8*(7-6/5^{\wedge}-4*3))*^*(2+1)$
-219212	$-9*(8+(7+6)*(5^4*3-2))+1$	-269917	$9*8*(7/6-5^{\wedge}4*3*2)-1$
-219214	$-9*(8+(7+6)*(5^4*3-2))-1$	-270085	$-9*8*(7/6+5^{\wedge}4*3*2)-1$
-219277	$98-(7+6)*5^4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-270141	$(9-8*(7+6/5^{\wedge}-4*3))*^*(2+1)$
-220587	$9/8*((7^{\wedge}6*-5+4)/3+2+1)$	-270195	$(-9-8*(7+6/5^{\wedge}-4*3))*^*(2+1)$
-223346	$(-9-8)*(7+6)*(5^4*3)*21$	-270359	$9*8*(7-(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*2)+1$
-224086	$9-(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)+3)/21$	-270361	$9*8*(7-(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*2)-1$
-224087	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4+3)/21$	-271334	$-98/7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
-224104	$-9-(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)+3)/21$	-271367	$9*-8*(7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*2)+1$
-225099	$-9-(8+7)*(6+5^{\wedge}4*(3+21))$	-271369	$9*-8*(7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*2)-1$
-225702	$9/8*(7-6-5^{\wedge}4*321)$	-271371	$(9-876)*((5^4+3)/2-1)$
-226710	$-9*((87-6)*(5^4-3)/2-1)$	-274179	$9-876*((5^4+3)/2-1)$
-231942	$-9*(8*7+6)*(5^4/3*2-1)$	-275485	$98+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
-232323	$(-9*87+6)*(5*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-275569	$98-7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
-232711	$9-8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4-321)$	-276131	$(-9-8)*(((7+6)*5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$
-232729	$-9-8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4-321)$	-276335	$(-9-8)*(((7+6)*5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$
-232749	$-9-8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4-321)$	-277005	$(-9-876)*((5^4+3)/2-1)$
-233058	$-9*(8*7+6)*(5^4/3*2+1)$	-277559	$(-9-8)*((7+6)*(5^4+3)*2-1)$
-234769	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5*43)*2+1$	-277593	$(-9-8)*((7+6)*(5^4+3)*2+1)$
-234775	$9-8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3*21)$	-278565	$(-98-7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3))*^*21$
-234793	$-9-8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3*21)$	-280601	$-98*7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)+21$
-234996	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)/4+321$	-280643	$-98*7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-21$
-235567	$9*(-8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*2)-1$	-280698	$-9*87-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)+21$
-235600	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4-321$	-280740	$-9*87-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)-21$
-235783	$9-8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3*21)$	-284388	$-9*(8+76*(5^4/3*2-1))$
-236005	$98+(7-6*5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	-286161	$(9+8)*(7*6-5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-236299	$98-(7+6*5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	-287589	$(-9-8)*(7*6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-236933	$9*(8-7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*2)+1$	-288666	$98/7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$
-237077	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*2)+1$	-290526	$9+(8+7)*(6-5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
-237079	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*2)-1$	-290706	$9-(8+7)*(6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
-237847	$9-8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+321)$	-292462	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3/2+1)$
-237865	$-9-8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+321)$	-292632	$9*-8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3/2+1)$
-237885	$-9-8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4+321)$	-293468	$(9-8*7)*(-6+5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-237935	$9+8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	-294032	$(9-8*7)*(6+5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-240914	$(9*8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*43)/-21$	-295613	$9*8-(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3/2+1)$
-242905	$(9*8-7)*((6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*2+1)$	-295757	$-9*8-(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3/2+1)$
-243035	$(9*8-7)*((6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*2-1)$	-295783	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3/2+1)$
-244465	$(9*-8+7)*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*2-1)$	-297277	$(9*8+7)*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*2-1)$
-244595	$(9*-8+7)*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*2+1)$	-302049	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*((5^4-3)*-2+1)$
-245497	$(9+8)/(7/(6^{\wedge}5*(-4-3^{\wedge}2+1)))$	-303825	$(-9/(8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))))^{\wedge}-1$
-247374	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-305451	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*((5^4+3)*-2-1)$
-249254	$(9+8)*(7+(6+5)^{\wedge}4/3)*(-2-1)$	-305732	$98+7/6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-249516	$9*87*-6*(54+3^{\wedge}-2-1)$	-306915	$-9/((8*76-54)/3)^{\wedge}-2+1$
-249804	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-306917	$-9/((8*76-54)/3)^{\wedge}-2-1$
-249954	$9*8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21$	-308832	$-9/8*(7^{\wedge}(6+5-4)/3+2+1)$
-250025	$9-8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21$	-309294	$-9+(8+7)*(6-5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$
-250069	$-9+8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21$	-312223	$9-8*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/3+21)$
-250085	$-9-8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21$	-312241	$-9-8*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/3+21)$
-250098	$-9*8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21$	-312807	$9+8*(7+6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
-250140	$-9*8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21$	-313227	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5-4*321)$
-251812	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-313607	$9-8*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)/3-21)$
-251943	$-9/(8+7)*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-313847	$9-8/7*(65^{\wedge}(4-3+2)-1)$
-251956	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-313905	$-9-8*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)/3+21)$
-252047	$9-8*7*(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	-313961	$-9-8*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)/3+21)$
-252174	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4-3)/21)$	-313965	$(9+8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))*^*(2+1)$
-253708	$(9+8)*(76-5^{\wedge}4*(3+21))$	-314019	$(-9+8*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))*^*(2+1)$
-254923	$9+(8-76)*(5^4*3*2-1)$	-315159	$9-8*(7-6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
-255795	$(9+876^{\wedge}(-5+4+3))/(-2-1)$	-315599	$-9-8*(76+5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
-256292	$(-9-8)*(76+5^{\wedge}4*(3+21))$	-317175	$9-8*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
-258029	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*(4+3)-2)+1$	-317193	$-9-8*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$
-260298	$-9*((87+6)*(5^4-3)/2-1)$	-320392	$(9/(8*7-(6+5)^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$
-260316	$-9*((87+6)*(5^4-3)/2+1)$	-324510	$9*-87*((65-4)/3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-264141	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-543*2-1)$	-326163	$(-98-76)*(5^4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-264306	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4)+321$	-327957	$(-9-8*(76+5^{\wedge}4*3))*^*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-328695	$9-8^{(-7+6+5)}/4*321$	-379491	$(-9-8)/(7/((6+5^{(4+3)})^*2-1))$
-328849	$98-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-381379	$9-(8+7^*(6^{(5+4)/3})^*21)$
-329045	$-98-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-382245	$(9+8)^*(7-6/5^{(4+3)^*2+1})$
-330533	$(98+7^{(6-5^4)^3})/21$	-382449	$(9+8)/(7/(6-5^{(4+3)^*2-1}))$
-330988	$(9^*8-76^*5^{(4/3)^*21})$	-382755	$(-9-8)^*(7+6/5^{(4+3)^*2+1})$
-331551	$(-9-8)^*(7^{(6-5^4)/3}/2-1)$	-385228	$(-9/(8+(7+6-5^{(4+3)^*2-1}))^{(2+1)})$
-331585	$(-9-8)^*(7^{(6-5^4)/3}/2+1)$	-386463	$98-7^{(6-5^4)/3}/21$
-331593	$(9+8^{(-7+6+5)/4})^*-321$	-386659	$-98-7^{(6-5^4)/3}/21$
-334012	$(-9^*8-76^*5^{(4/3)^*21})$	-387168	$(-9-87)/65^*(4^{(3+2+1)})$
-334747	$(-9-8)^*(7+6-5-4)^{3/2-1}$	-389739	$9+876-5^{(4+3)/2}+1$
-339874	$(9/(8-7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)})^{(2+1)}$	-389741	$9+876-5^{(4+3)/2}-1$
-339991	$9+(8-76)^*5^{(4/3)^*2-1}$	-389757	$-9+876-5^{(4+3)/2}+1$
-340009	$-9+(8-76)^*5^{(4/3)^*2-1}$	-389759	$-9+876-5^{(4+3)/2}-1$
-342516	$9^*-876^*((5^4/3)^{2-1})$	-390381	$9^{(8+7)/6}-5^{(4+3)/2}+1$
-345999	$-9^*(8-7/6)^*(5^{(4+3)^*2+1})$	-390383	$9^{(8+7)/6}-5^{(4+3)/2}-1$
-347224	$98-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-391398	$(9-87^*(6+5^{(4/3)^*21}))$
-348648	$9-(87+6)^*(5^{(4+3)^*2-1})$	-391493	$9-876-5^{(4+3)/2}-1$
-348666	$-9-(87+6)^*(5^{(4+3)^*2-1})$	-391511	$-9-876-5^{(4+3)/2}-1$
-350399	$-9^*876/(5^4/3)^{2-1}$	-391578	$9-87^*(6+5^{(4/3)^*21})$
-350401	$-9^*876/(5^4/3)^{2-1}$	-391596	$-9-87^*(6+5^{(4/3)^*21})$
-350955	$-9^*(8+(7^{(6-5^4)/3}-21))$	-391776	$(-9-87^*(6+5^{(4/3)^*21}))$
-350965	$98-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-392082	$98-(7^{(6+5)^*4-(3/2)^{2-1}})$
-351179	$-98-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-392108	$9^*8-(7^{(6+5)^*4-(3/2)^{2-1}})$
-351301	$9+8-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-392252	$9^*8-(7^{(6+5)^*4-(3/2)^{2-1}})$
-352085	$-98-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-392278	$-98-(7^{(6+5)^*4-(3/2)^{2-1}})$
-352171	$(9-8^*7)^*(6/5^{(4-3)^*2-1})$	-396312	$-98^*((7+6)^*(5^{(4+3)/2+1}))$
-352204	$98-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-398898	$-9/8^*(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-352400	$-98-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-399942	$(9+8)^*(7^{(6-5^4)^3}-3+2)^{2-1}$
-353494	$98-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-399980	$(-98/7-6)^*(5^{(4+3)^*2-1})$
-353500	$9^*8-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-400020	$(-98/7-6)^*(5^{(4+3)^*2+1})$
-353644	$-9^*8-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-400078	$(9+8)^*(7^{(6-5^4)^3}-3+2)^{2-1}$
-353670	$-98-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-404272	$(-9-8^{(7+6)})/((6+5)/(4/3)^{2-1})$
-353690	$-98-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-406461	$(9-8^*7^6)^*(5^{(4+3)^*2-1})$
-354005	$-98-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-406686	$(9-(87+6)^*5^{(4/3)^*21})$
-354145	$(9-8^*7)^*(6^*(5^{(4+3)^*2-1}))$	-407064	$(9+(87+6)^*5^{(4/3)^*21})$
-354481	$9^*-8/(7/6+5+4^{(3)^*2-1})$	-407904	$(9+87)^*(6-5^{(4/3)^*21})$
-354559	$9+8-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-409486	$98-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-354575	$9-8-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-409512	$9^*8-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-354577	$-9+8-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-409656	$9^*8-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-354593	$-9-8-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-409682	$-98-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-354636	$-9^*(8+(7-6+5^{(4+3)^*21}))$	-410385	$(9-8^*7^6)^*(5^{(4+3)^*2-1})$
-354705	$-9^*(8+(7^{(6+5^4)^3}/3-21))$	-411039	$(9-8^*7^6)^*(5^{(4+3)^*2+1})$
-354715	$98-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-411668	$9^*8-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-354929	$-98-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-411670	$98-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-354939	$9^*(8-(7^{(6+5^4)^3}/3-21))$	-411677	$98-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-355212	$-9^*(87+6+5^{(4+3)^*21})$	-411696	$9^*8-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-355374	$9^*(8+7-(6+5^{(4+3)^*21}))$	-411798	$-9+(8/(7^{(6+5^4)^3}/(4-32)))^{2-1}$
-355518	$-9^*(8-7+(6+5^{(4+3)^*21}))$	-411847	$9^*8-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-356155	$(9-8^*(7+6))^*(5^{(4+3)^*2-1})$	-411866	$-98-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-356345	$(9-8^*(7+6))^*(5^{(4+3)^*2+1})$	-411873	$-98-(7^{(6-5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-358288	$-98^*((7^{(6-5^4)^3}/32-1))$	-411875	$-9^*8-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-358474	$98-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-412657	$9^*(87-(6+5^{(4/3)^*2+1}))$
-358484	$-98^*((7^{(6-5^4)^3}/32+1))$	-412675	$9^*(87-(6+5^{(4/3)^*2-1}))$
-358670	$-98-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-412944	$9^*(8^*7-(6+5^{(4/3)^*2+1}))$
-362117	$(9-876)^*(5^{(4/3)^*2+1})$	-412946	$9^*(8^*7-(6+5^{(4/3)^*2-1}))$
-364115	$9-876^*(5^{(4/3)^*2-1})$	-413583	$-9^*(8+7+(6+5^{(4/3)^*2+1}))$
-364133	$-9-876^*(5^{(4/3)^*2-1})$	-413585	$-9^*(8+7+(6+5^{(4/3)^*2-1}))$
-365867	$9-876^*(5^{(4/3)^*2+1})$	-413672	$9^*8^*-7^*((6^*5-4/3)^{2-1})$
-365885	$-9-876^*(5^{(4/3)^*2+1})$	-413861	$98-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-367652	$9/8-7^{(6-5^4)^3}/4^*(3/2+1)$	-413887	$9^*8-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-367657	$9^*(87-(6-5^{(4/3)^*2+1}))$	-413916	$(-9-8)^*((7+6)^*(5^{(4+3)^*2-1}))$
-367675	$9^*(87-(6-5^{(4/3)^*2-1}))$	-413950	$(-9-8)^*((7+6)^*(5^{(4+3)^*2+1}))$
-367944	$9^*(8^*7-(6-5^{(4/3)^*2+1}))$	-413954	$-9^*(8^*7+(6+5^{(4/3)^*2-1}))$
-367946	$9^*(8^*7-(6-5^{(4/3)^*2-1}))$	-414031	$-9^*8-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-368315	$9^*(8+7-(6-5^{(4/3)^*2-1}))$	-414057	$-98-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$
-368583	$-9^*(8+7+(6-5^{(4/3)^*2+1}))$	-414223	$-9^*(87+(6+5^{(4/3)^*2-1}))$
-368585	$-9^*(8+7+(6-5^{(4/3)^*2-1}))$	-414241	$-9^*(87+(6+5^{(4/3)^*2+1}))$
-368952	$-9^*(8^*7+(6-5^{(4/3)^*2+1}))$	-414392	$(9+8)^*((7+6)/(5^{(4-4/3)}-3)-2+1)$
-368954	$-9^*(8^*7+(6-5^{(4/3)^*2-1}))$	-414426	$(-9-8)^*((7+6)^*5^{(4+3)^*2+1})$
-369223	$-9^*(87+(6-5^{(4/3)^*2-1}))$	-414680	$9^*8^*-7^*((6^*5-4/3)^{2+1})$
-369635	$(-9-876)^*(5^{(4/3)^*2+1})$	-414800	$(-9-8)^*((7+6)^*(5^{(4+3)^*2-1}))$
-377045	$-98-(7^{(6+5^4)^3})^{*(2+1)}$	-416245	$(-9-8)/(7/((6^*(5+4^3))^2-1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-418324	$(9/8/((7^6+5)^{-4+3/2}))^{-1}$	-498925	$98 - (7/(6-5^4 \cdot 3)^2)^{-1}$
-427614	$(9^*8+7^*6)^*(5^4 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 2^{-1})$	-499121	$-98 - (7/(6-5^4 \cdot 3)^2)^{-1}$
-428835	$(9+8^*7^*6)^*((-5^4+3)^2+1)$	-499528	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5)/4-3^{(2+1)})$
-429525	$(9+8^*7^*6)^*((-5^4+3)^2-1)$	-499624	$(9+8/76)/(5-43)^{(-2-1)}$
-431300	$98 - (7^6+5)^*(4/3^2+1)$	-499817	$(9+8)^*((7^6-5)/-4+3^2+1)$
-431470	$9^*8 - (7^6+5)^*(4/3^2+1)$	-499868	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5)/4-3^2-1)$
-432975	$(9+8^*7^*6)^*((5^4+3)^{-2+1})$	-499953	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5)/4-3+2-1)$
-434469	$9+87^*(6-5^4 \cdot (3^2-1))$	-500106	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5)/4+3^2+1)$
-434487	$-9+87^*(6-5^4 \cdot (3^2-1))$	-500123	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5)/4+3^2-1)$
-437054	$-9^*8-7^6 \cdot (5/(4+3)+2+1)$	-500191	$-98 - (7/(6/54))^3 \cdot 2+1$
-438677	$9^*(8-(7+6)/5^4-4^3 \cdot 2)+1$	-500193	$-98 - (7/(6/54))^3 \cdot 2-1$
-438679	$9^*(8-(7+6)/5^4-4^3 \cdot 2)-1$	-500446	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5)/4+3^{(2+1)})$
-438821	$-9^*(8+(7+6)/5^4-4^3 \cdot 2)+1$	-509817	$(98-(7+6)^5 \cdot 4^3)^*21$
-438823	$-9^*(8+(7+6)/5^4-4^3 \cdot 2)-1$	-511698	$9+(8-(7+6)^5 \cdot 4^3)^*21$
-444099	$9+(8-7^*6)^*(5^4-3)^*21$	-520910	$9^*(8-(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-444117	$-9+(8-7^*6)^*(5^4-3)^*21$	-520912	$9^*(8-(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-444452	$(-9/(8^*7^6 \cdot (5/4+3)+2))^{-1}$	-521054	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-444805	$(9+8)^*(7^*(6-5^4 \cdot 3)^2+1)$	-521056	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-447661	$(9+8)^*(7^*(6+5^4 \cdot 3)^{-2+1})$	-522790	$98+(7^6 \cdot 5+4)^*(3^4-2-1)$
-447695	$(9+8)^*(7^*(6+5^4 \cdot 3)^{-2-1})$	-522816	$9^*8+(7^6 \cdot 5+4)^*(3^4-2-1)$
-450909	$98 - (7^6+5)^*(4-(3^2)^{-1})$	-522986	$-98+(7^6 \cdot 5+4)^*(3^4-2-1)$
-450935	$9^*8 - (7^6+5)^*(4-(3^2)^{-1})$	-524637	$9^*(8+(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)^*(-5^*432+1)$
-451079	$9^*8 - (7^6+5)^*(4-(3^2)^{-1})$	-525123	$9^*(8+(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)^*(-5^*432-1)$
-451105	$-98 - (7^6+5)^*(4-(3^2)^{-1})$	-526914	$9^*(8-(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2-1)$
-455800	$-9^*8-7/6^*(5^4 \cdot (3/2)^{-1})$	-527634	$(-98+(7^6-5)/4)^*(3-21)$
-457232	$((-9-8)/(7-65^4 \cdot 3)^2)^{-1}$	-528233	$(9-8^*7)^*(6^*(5^4 \cdot 3-2)+1)$
-463980	$-9^*(8+7/6)^*(5^4 \cdot 3^2-1)$	-528410	$9^*(8-(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-464991	$9-(87+6)^*5^4 \cdot (3^2-1)$	-528412	$9^*(8-(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-467998	$98 - (7^6-5^4)^*(3+2-1)$	-528534	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-468168	$9^*8 - (7^6-5^4)^*(3+2-1)$	-528554	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-468423	$9-8^*((7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2+1)$	-528556	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-468425	$-9-8^*((7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2-1)$	-528609	$(9^*(-8-7)-6)^*(5^4 \cdot 3^2-1)$
-468441	$-9-8^*((7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2+1)$	-528797	$(9-8^*7)^*(6^*(5^4 \cdot 3^2-1))$
-469931	$9-8^*((7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2-1)$	-529037	$9^*(8-(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-469947	$9-8^*((7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2+1)$	-529082	$9^*(8-(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-470405	$-9-8^*((7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2-1)$	-529084	$9^*(8-(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-470409	$-9-8^*((7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2+1)$	-529101	$9^*(8-(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2-1)$
-470418	$98 - (7^6-5^4)^*(3+2-1)$	-529183	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-470462	$98 - (7^6-5^4)^*(3+2-1)$	-529267	$(9-8^*7)^*(6^*(5^4 \cdot 3^2-1))$
-470774	$-98 - (7^6+5^4)^*(3+2-1)$	-529319	$9^*(8-(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-470787	$9-8^*((7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2+1)$	-529333	$9^*(8-(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-471227	$9-8^*((7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2-1)$	-529508	$-9^*(8+(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-471243	$9-8^*((7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2+1)$	-529522	$-9^*(8+(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-471261	$-9-8^*((7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2+1)$	-529523	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-471439	$9-8^*((7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2-1)$	-529525	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-471473	$-9-8^*((7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2+1)$	-529570	$-9^*(8+(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-472051	$9^*(8-7^*(6/5^4-4^3)^2)-1$	-529658	$9^*(8-(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-472193	$-9^*(8+7^*(6/5^4-4^3)^2)+1$	-529660	$9^*(8-(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-472195	$-9^*(8+7^*(6/5^4-4^3)^2)-1$	-529757	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-472481	$9^*(8-(7^6/5^4-4^3)^2)+1$	-529759	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-472625	$-9^*(8+(7^6/5^4-4^3)^2)+1$	-529802	$-9^*(8+(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-472627	$-9^*(8+(7^6/5^4-4^3)^2)-1$	-529804	$-9^*(8+(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-472751	$9-8^*((7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2-1)$	-530285	$9^*(8-(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-472769	$-9-8^*((7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2-1)$	-530287	$9^*(8-(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-472785	$-9-8^*((7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2+1)$	-530429	$-9^*(8+(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-472805	$9^*(8-7^*(6/5^4-4^3)^2)+1$	-530451	$-9^*(8+(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-472807	$9^*(8-7^*(6/5^4-4^3)^2)-1$	-531783	$9^*(8-(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2+1)$
-472949	$-9^*(8+7^*(6/5^4-4^3)^2)+1$	-534280	$(9-8^*(7+6))^*(5^4 \cdot 3^2-1)$
-472951	$-9^*(8+7^*(6/5^4-4^3)^2)-1$	-534470	$(9-8^*(7+6))^*(5^4 \cdot 3^2+1)$
-473024	$9^*8 - (7^6+5^4)^*(3+2-1)$	-536903	$9^*8^*(7-6^*(5^4-3)^2)+1$
-473168	$-9^*8 - (7^6+5^4)^*(3+2-1)$	-536905	$9^*8^*(7-6^*(5^4-3)^2)-1$
-473194	$-98 - (7^6+5^4)^*(3+2-1)$	-537785	$9^*(8-(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)+1$
-474695	$9^*(8-7^6 \cdot (5^4+3)^2)+1$	-537913	$9^*8^*(7-6^*(5^4-3)^2)-1$
-474697	$9^*(8-7^6 \cdot (5^4+3)^2)-1$	-537931	$-9^*(8+(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/2)-1$
-474839	$-9^*(8+7^6 \cdot (5^4+3)^2)+1$	-542087	$9^*8^*(7-6^*(5^4+3)^2)+1$
-474841	$-9^*(8+7^6 \cdot (5^4+3)^2)-1$	-542089	$9^*8^*(7-6^*(5^4+3)^2)-1$
-483621	$(9^*(-8-7)+6)^*(5^4 \cdot 3^2-1)$	-542491	$9 - ((8+7)^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/21$
-485095	$(9^*8-7)^*(-6^*(5^4-3)^2+1)$	-542509	$-9 - ((8+7)^6+5^4 \cdot 3)/21$
-485225	$(9^*8-7)^*(-6^*(5^4-3)^2-1)$	-543095	$9^*8^*(7-6^*(5^4+3)^2)+1$
-490950	$-9-87^*(6+5^4 \cdot 3)^*(2+1)$	-543097	$9^*8^*(7-6^*(5^4+3)^2)-1$
-494530	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5)/4-321)$	-543219	$9+87^*(6-5^4 \cdot (3^2+1))$
-494595	$9^*-87^*(6+5^4 \cdot (3/2)^{-1})$	-543237	$-9+87^*(6-5^4 \cdot (3^2+1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-548702	$-98 \cdot 7 \cdot 6^*(5^4-3) \cdot 21$	-655375	$98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4 \cdot 3/21)$
-548954	$98 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+(3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-655536	$9 \cdot 87^*(6^*(5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 2-1)$
-548980	$9^*8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+(3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-655571	$-98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4 \cdot 3/21)$
-548996	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4 \cdot 3)/21$	-655710	$9 \cdot 87^*(6^*(5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 2+1)$
-549038	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4 \cdot 3)/21$	-659391	$9 \cdot (8^*7-6)^*(5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 21$
-549124	$9^* \cdot 8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+(3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-661410	$-9/8^*(7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5-4-321)$
-549150	$-98 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+(3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-661473	$-9/(8/((7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(3+2)+1))$
-550172	$98^*(-7+(6 \cdot 5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)^*(2+1))$	-661803	$-9/8^*(7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5+43)+21$
-550711	$98 \cdot 7^*(6^*5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 21$	-661845	$-9/8^*(7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5+43) \cdot 21$
-551789	$-98 \cdot 7^*(6^*5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 21$	-663085	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/3-2-1)$
-552328	$98^*(7-(6+5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)^*(2+1))$	-663187	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)/3+2+1)$
-553700	$-98^*(7+(6+5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)^*(2+1))$	-663799	$9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 321)$
-553798	$98 \cdot 7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 21$	-663817	$-9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 321)$
-553994	$-98 \cdot 7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 21$	-666621	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)/-3+2+1)$
-558842	$-9+(8/(7^{\wedge}6^*(5-43)-2))^{\wedge}-1$	-666740	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)/-3+2+1)$
-563928	$9^*(8-(7^*6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-666842	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)/-3-2-1)$
-563930	$9^*(8-(7^*6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	-670072	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^*(6+5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-564072	$-9^*(8+(7^*6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-670106	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^*(6+5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-564074	$-9^*(8+(7^*6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	-670667	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(76+5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^*21)$
-564237	$(-9/(8+(7+6)^*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)))^{\wedge}-1$	-672103	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5/(4+3)-21)$
-569383	$9 \cdot 8^*76^*(5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3/2-1)$	-672121	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5/(4+3)-21)$
-570599	$9 \cdot 8^*76^*(5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3/2+1)$	-672439	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5/(4+3)+21)$
-570843	$(9+8)^*(7+6/5)^*(-4^{\wedge}(3^*2)+1)$	-672457	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5/(4+3)+21)$
-576312	$-9^*8+7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5^*(4+3)^{\wedge}-2-1$	-679957	$9+(8-7^*6)^*(5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 32-1)$
-581241	$9 \cdot (87+6)^*5^{\wedge}4^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-680025	$9+(8-7^*6)^*(5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 32+1)$
-589577	$(-9 \cdot 8-7)^*(6^*(5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 2-1)$	-680043	$-9+(8-7^*6)^*(5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 32+1)$
-592524	$-9 \cdot (8+7)^*(6+5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3) \cdot 21$	-681649	$-9^*8 \cdot (7+6)/(5/(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-595265	$(-9^*8-7)^*(6^*(5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 2-1)$	-702428	$(9 \cdot (8^*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*(3+2-1)$
-595423	$(-9^*8-7)^*(6^*(5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 2+1)$	-702500	$(9+(8^*7)^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^*(-3-2+1)$
-599088	$9 \cdot (8^{\wedge}7 \cdot 6-5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)/21$	-703512	$(98 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^*(3+21)$
-599106	$-9 \cdot (8^{\wedge}7 \cdot 6-5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)/21$	-704394	$9^*(8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^*21)$
-600152	$98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5^*(4+3)^{\wedge}-2+1$	-704538	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^*21)$
-600178	$9^*8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5^*(4+3)^{\wedge}-2+1$	-704565	$9^*(87-6^*(5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 21)$
-600322	$9^* \cdot 8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5^*(4+3)^{\wedge}-2+1$	-705213	$9^*(8+7-6^*(5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 21)$
-612402	$98^*(7-6-5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-705357	$-9^*(8-7+6^*(5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 21)$
-613774	$-98^*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-705417	$9^*((8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)/3)^*2+1)$
-615538	$-9/87^*(65^{\wedge}4/3+2)+1$	-705435	$9^*((8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)/3)^*2-1)$
-615539	$-9/87^*(65^{\wedge}4/3+2)/1$	-705489	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)/3^*2+1)$
-615540	$-9/87^*(65^{\wedge}4/3+2)-1$	-705507	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)/3^*2-1)$
-616616	$-98^*(7^*6+5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-705633	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)/3^*2-1)$
-617470	$98 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3) \cdot 21$	-705651	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)/3^*2+1)$
-617596	$98 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3) \cdot 21$	-705723	$-9^*((8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)/3)^*2+1)$
-617666	$-98 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4-3) \cdot 21$	-706065	$9^*((8-(7^{\wedge}6+54)/3)^*2+1)$
-617792	$-98 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3) \cdot 21$	-706107	$9 \cdot (8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)/4)^*(3+21)$
-617853	$9 \cdot (8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3) \cdot 21$	-706133	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5)^*(4/3+2)+1$
-617871	$-9 \cdot (8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3) \cdot 21$	-706135	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5)^*(4/3+2)-1$
-626183	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^*21)$	-706137	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+54)/3^*2+1)$
-626201	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3^*21)$	-706281	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)/3^*2-1)$
-626911	$9+8^*(7-6^*(5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 21)$	-706299	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)/3^*2+1)$
-626929	$-9+8^*(7-6^*(5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 21)$	-706353	$-9^*((8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)/3)^*2-1)$
-627023	$9 \cdot 8^*(7+6^*(5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 21)$	-707400	$9^*(87-(6^*5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 21)$
-629431	$9+8^*(7-(6^*5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 21)$	-707921	$9^*(8-7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3-2))+1$
-630439	$9+8^*(7-(6^*5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 21)$	-707923	$9^*(8-7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3-2))-1$
-632959	$9+8^*(7-6^*(5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 21)$	-708065	$-9^*(8+7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3-2))+1$
-633071	$9 \cdot 8^*(7+6^*(5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 21)$	-708067	$-9^*(8+7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3-2))-1$
-638911	$98^*(7^*(6-5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3/2)+1)$	-708216	$(98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^*(-3-21)$
-639107	$98^*(7^*(6-5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3/2)-1)$	-708276	$(98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)/4)^*(-3-21)$
-640638	$-9^*(8+76^*(5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3/2-1))$	-709433	$9^*(8-7^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3+2))+1$
-641205	$9^*((8-76^*5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)/2+1)$	-711359	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4(4+3))^*2)+1$
-642006	$-9^*(8+76^*(5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3/2+1))$	-711361	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4(4+3))^*2)-1$
-645085	$-98^*(7^*(6+5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)/2-1)$	-711503	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4(4+3))^*2)+1$
-645281	$-98^*(7^*(6+5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3)/2+1)$	-711505	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4(4+3))^*2)-1$
-645840	$(9+8^*7^*6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*-3+2+1)$	-712287	$-9^*(8+7+6^*(5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 21)$
-646530	$(9+8^*7^*6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*-3+2-1)$	-712935	$-9^*(87+6^*(5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 21)$
-648837	$9 \cdot 87^*6^*((5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 2-1)$	-723807	$9/(8/7-6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-649272	$-9 \cdot 87^*(6^*(5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 2-1)$	-730405	$(9^*8-7)^*(6^*(5^{\wedge}4^*-3+2)+1)$
-649290	$-9 \cdot 87^*(6^*(5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 2-1)$	-730535	$(9^*8-7)^*(6^*(5^{\wedge}4^*-3+2)-1)$
-649881	$9 \cdot 87^*6^*((5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 2+1)$	-730688	$98^*(7-6^*(5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 2+1)$
-649899	$-9 \cdot 87^*6^*((5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 2+1)$	-731127	$9+8^*7^*(6-(5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 21)$
-652926	$9 \cdot 87^*((6^*5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 2-1)$	-731374	$98^*(7-6^*((5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 2+1))$
-653682	$9^* \cdot 8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5+4)^*(3^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-731570	$-98^*(7+6^*((5^{\wedge}4-3) \cdot 2-1))$
-655101	$9 \cdot 87^*6^*((5^{\wedge}4+3) \cdot 2-1)$	-731965	$(9^*8-7)^*(-6^*(5^{\wedge}4 \cdot 3+2)+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-732256	$-98*(7+6*(5^4-3))^*2+1$	-821653	$(9*8-(7^6-54)/3)^*21$
-738183	$9+8*7*(6-(5^4+3))^*21$	-822117	$9-876*(5^4*3/2+1)$
-738626	$-98*(7+6*((5^4+3)^*2-1))$	-822135	$-9-876*(5^4*3/2+1)$
-738855	$9-8*7*(6+(5^4+3))^*21$	-822409	$(9*8-(7^6+54)/3)^*21$
-739116	$-98*(7+6*(5^4+3))^*2-1$	-822600	$9*(-8+7*(6-(5^4-3))^*21))$
-739312	$-98*(7+6*(5^4+3))^*2+1$	-822808	$(9+8-(7^6-54)/3)^*21$
-750108	$9+(8-(7/(6/54)))^3)^*(2+1)$	-822988	$9+(8-(7^6-54)/3)^*21$
-750156	$9-(8+(7/(6/54)))^3)^*(2+1)$	-823144	$(9-8-(7^6-54)/3)^*21$
-750213	$-9*(8+(7/(6/54)))^3/(2+1))$	-823226	$9+(8-(7^6-5^4)/3)^*21$
-756054	$9*(8-7^6*5/(4+3)+21)$	-823303	$9+(8-(7^6-5-4)/3)^*21$
-756198	$-9*(8+7^6*5/(4+3)-21)$	-823321	$-9+(8-(7^6-5-4)/3)^*21$
-756351	$9-8*(76*(5^4-3))^*2+1$	-823324	$9-(8+(7^6-54)/3)^*21$
-756353	$-9-8*(76*(5^4-3))^*2-1$	-823342	$-9-(8+(7^6-54)/3)^*21$
-756432	$9*(8-7^6*5/(4+3)-21)$	-823359	$9+(8-(7^6-5+4)/3)^*21$
-759132	$9^((8+7)/6)*(5^4*(-3-2)+1)$	-823373	$9+(8-(7^6+5-4)/3)^*21$
-759618	$9^((8+7)/6)*(5^4*(-3-2)-1)$	-823377	$-9+(8-(7^6-5+4)/3)^*21$
-763647	$9-8*(76*(5^4+3))^*2+1$	-823429	$9+(8-(7^6+5+4)/3)^*21$
-764588	$98-(7^6-5)*(4+3/2+1)$	-823657	$-9-(8+(7^6-5-4)/3)^*21$
-764614	$9*8-(7^6-5)*(4+3/2+1)$	-823709	$9-(8+(7^6+5-4)/3)^*21$
-764653	$98-(7^6+5)*(4+3/2+1)$	-823713	$-9-(8+(7^6-5+4)/3)^*21$
-764679	$9*8-(7^6+5)*(4+3/2+1)$	-823744	$9+(8-(7^6+54)/3)^*21$
-764758	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*(4+3/2+1))$	-823762	$-9+(8-(7^6+54)/3)^*21$
-764784	$-98-(7^6-5)*(4+3/2+1)$	-823765	$9-(8+(7^6+5+4)/3)^*21$
-764823	$9*-8-(7^6+5)*(4+3/2+1)$	-823822	$9*(8+7^6/5)*(-4+3^2-2)+1$
-768663	$9*((8-76)*(5^4+3))^*2+1$	-823824	$9*(8+7^6/5)*(-4+3^2-2)-1$
-768681	$9*((8-76)*(5^4+3))^*2-1$	-823842	$9-(8+(7^6+5^4)/3)^*21$
-776183	$9-8*(7^6-5^4*(32+1))$	-823860	$-9-(8+(7^6+5^4)/3)^*21$
-776201	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4*(32+1))$	-823942	$(9-8+(7^6+54)/3)^*-21$
-781175	$9-8*(7^6-5^4*32-1)$	-824098	$-9-(8+(7^6+54)/3)^*21$
-786183	$9-8*(7^6-5^4*(32-1))$	-824278	$(9+8+(7^6+54)/3)^*-21$
-786201	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4*(32-1))$	-824677	$(9*8+(7^6-54)/3)^*-21$
-793692	$9*((8-(7^6-5)/4)^*3+21)$	-825461	$(98+(7^6-5^4)/3)^*-21$
-793836	$9*(8-(7^6-5)/4)^*3+21$	-825538	$(98+(7^6-5-4)/3)^*-21$
-793862	$9*((8-(7^6-5)/4)^*3+2)+1$	-825608	$(98+(7^6+5-4)/3)^*-21$
-793864	$9*((8-(7^6-5)/4)^*3+2)-1$	-825664	$(98+(7^6+5+4)/3)^*-21$
-793900	$9*((8-(7^6-5)/4)^*3-2)-1$	-825741	$(98+(7^6+5^4)/3)^*-21$
-793980	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)/4)^*3-21$	-825860	$(98-(7^6+5^4)/3)^*21$
-793999	$98-(7^6-5)/4^3*(2+1)$	-826866	$9-(8+7+6)*5^4*3^2*21$
-794092	$9*(8-(7^6+5)/4)^*3+2^2-1$	-827741	$9+(8-(7^6+5^4)/3)^*21$
-794093	$9*(8-(7^6+5)/4)^*3-2^2-1$	-827759	$-9+(8-(7^6+5^4)/3)^*21$
-794139	$-9-(8/(7^6*54-3^2))^2-1$	-828077	$9-(8+(7^6+5^4)/3)^*21$
-794143	$(-98-7^6*54)/(3^2-1)$	-828095	$-9-(8+(7^6+5^4)/3)^*21$
-794195	$-98-(7^6-5)/4^3*(2+1)$	-828529	$(-9-8)*(7+6)*(5^4*3^2-1)$
-794236	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)/4)^*3+2^2-1$	-828733	$(-9-8)*((7+6)*5^4*3^2-1)$
-794237	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)/4)^*3-2^2-1$	-828767	$(-9-8)*((7+6)*5^4*3^2+1)$
-794294	$9*((8+(7^6-5)/4)^*3-2)+1$	-828971	$(-9-8)*(7+6)*(5^4*3^2+1)$
-794330	$-9*((8+(7^6-5)/4)^*3+2)+1$	-829134	$-9*876*(5^4/3/2+1)$
-794332	$-9*((8+(7^6-5)/4)^*3+2)-1$	-829976	$(98+(7^6+5^4)/3)^*-21$
-794358	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)/4)^*3+21$	-830538	$9*(-8+7*(6-(5^4+3))^*21))$
-794502	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)/4)^*3+21$	-835679	$9-8*(7^6-(5^4+3))^*21$
-809477	$9*(8*(7-6/5^4-4^3)+2)+1$	-835697	$-9-8*(7^6-(5^4+3))^*21$
-809479	$9*(8*(7-6/5^4-4^3)+2)-1$	-836687	$9-8*(7^6-(5^4-3))^*21$
-809513	$9*(8*(7-6/5^4-4^3)-2)+1$	-836705	$-9-8*(7^6-(5^4-3))^*21$
-809515	$9*(8*(7-6/5^4-4^3)-2)-1$	-839860	$98-7*6*(5^4*32-1)$
-809835	$9-(8*7+6)*(5^4-3)^*21$	-839909	$98-7*(6*5^4*32+1)$
-810470	$(9/(8-7^6*(5^4*3+2)))^2-1$	-840091	$-98-7*(6*5^4*32-1)$
-810485	$-9*(8*(7+6/5^4-4^3)-2)+1$	-840140	$-98-7*6*(5^4*32+1)$
-810487	$-9*(8*(7+6/5^4-4^3)-2)-1$	-850284	$-9*(8+76*((5^4-3)^*2-1))$
-810521	$-9*(8*(7+6/5^4-4^3)+2)+1$	-851183	$9-8*(7^6+5^4*(3-21))$
-810523	$-9*(8*(7+6/5^4-4^3)+2)-1$	-851201	$-9-8*(7^6+5^4*(3-21))$
-813366	$-9*876*(5^4/3/2-1)$	-851652	$-9*(8+76*((5^4-3)^*2+1))$
-817647	$9-(8*7+6)*(5^4+3)^*21$	-857229	$-9*(8+76*(5^4-3)/21)$
-818991	$9+(8-(7^6-5^4)/3)^*21$	-858492	$-9*(8+76*((5^4+3)^*2-1))$
-819009	$-9+(8-(7^6-5^4)/3)^*21$	-859860	$-9*(8+76*((5^4+3)^*2+1))$
-820605	$-9*(8+7/(6/(5^4(4+3)+21)))$	-871906	$-98*7*(6*5^4/3+21)$
-821201	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4*(3+21))$	-873144	$9*(8-7^6+5^4*(32+1))$
-821226	$(98+(7^6-5^4)/3)^*-21$	-875862	$(9-87)*(6*5^4*3-21)$
-821345	$(98-(7^6-5^4)/3)^*21$	-878778	$9*(8-7^6+5^4*32-1)$
-821422	$(98-(7^6-5-4)/3)^*21$	-878922	$-9*(8+7^6-5^4*32+1)$
-821478	$(98-(7^6-5+4)/3)^*21$	-879138	$(9-87)*(6*5^4*3+21)$
-821492	$(98-(7^6+5-4)/3)^*21$	-880092	$-9*87*6*(5^4/3-21)$
-821548	$(98-(7^6+5+4)/3)^*21$	-880910	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4(4+3))/2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-880912	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4(4+3)))/2-1$	-967329	$(98-(7^6-5)/4)*(32+1)$
-881054	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4(4+3)))/2+1$	-970465	$98-(7^6-5)/4*(32+1)$
-881056	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4(4+3)))/2-1$	-970661	$-98-(7^6-5)/4*(32+1)$
-882232	$98-(7^6-5)*(4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-970818	$9-(8+(7^6-5)/4)*(32+1)$
-882258	$9*8-(7^6-5)*(4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-970836	$-9-(8+(7^6-5)/4)*(32+1)$
-882333	$9*8-(7^6+5)*(4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-973797	$(98+(7^6-5)/4)*(-32-1)$
-882402	$-9*8-(7^6-5)*(4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-976914	$9-87*(6*5^4*3-21)$
-882477	$-9*8-(7^6+5)*(4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-976932	$-9-87*(6*5^4*3-21)$
-882503	$-98-(7^6+5)*(4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-977610	$9-87*(6*(5^4*3-2)-1)$
-884394	$9*(8-7^6+5^4*(32-1))$	-977628	$-9-87*(6*(5^4*3-2)-1)$
-884538	$-9*(8+7^6-5^4*(32-1))$	-977784	$9-87*(6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$
-887723	$(9*8+7)*(-6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$	-977802	$-9-87*(6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$
-887881	$(9*8+7)*(-6*(5^4*3-2)-1)$	-978654	$9-87*(6*5^4*3-2+1)$
-888199	$(-9-8)*(7*6*(5^4-3)*2-1)$	-979716	$-9-87*(6*(5^4*3+2)-1)$
-888233	$(-9-8)*(7*6*(5^4-3)*2+1)$	-982268	$9*(8-(7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-888335	$(-9-8)*7*(6*(5^4-3)*2+1)$	-982270	$9*(8-(7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-889619	$(9*8+7)*(6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$	-982412	$-9*(8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-891769	$(-9-8)*(7*(6*5^4-3)*2-1)$	-982414	$-9*(8+(7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-891803	$(-9-8)*(7*(6*5^4-3)*2+1)$	-984062	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^4*3)/2-1)$
-892428	$9+((8-76)*5^4+3)*21$	-984096	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^4*3)/2+1)$
-892446	$-9+((8-76)*5^4+3)*21$	-989703	$9-87*6*(5^4*3+21)$
-892554	$9+((8-76)*5^4-3)*21$	-989721	$-9-87*6*(5^4*3+21)$
-892572	$-9+((8-76)*5^4-3)*21$	-993870	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-892585	$(-9-8)*((7*6*5^4+3)*2-1)$	-995384	$(-9-8)*((7^6-543)/2-1)$
-892619	$(-9-8)*((7*6*5^4+3)*2+1)$	-996786	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-893197	$(-9-8)*(7*(6*5^4+3)*2-1)$	-997991	$9-(876-5^4*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-893231	$(-9-8)*(7*(6*5^4+3)*2+1)$	-997993	$9-(876-5^4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-894740	$(-98+7/6)*5*(43^{\wedge}2-1)$	-998009	$-9-(876-5^4*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-896665	$(-9-8)*7*(6*(5^4+3)*2-1)$	-998011	$-9-(876-5^4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-896767	$(-9-8)*(7*6*(5^4+3)*2-1)$	-999413	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5-4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
-896801	$(-9-8)*(7*6*(5^4+3)*2+1)$	-999447	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5-4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$
-896903	$(-9-8)*7*(6*(5^4+3)*2+1)$	-999498	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5-4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
-901975	$(9/(8-7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-2))^{\wedge}-1$	-999736	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5*(4+3))/2+1)$
-908703	$(98-(7^6-5)/4)*(32-1)$	-999770	$(-9-8)*((7^6-(5+4)*3)/2-1)$
-911484	$9+(8-(7^6-5)/4)*(32-1)$	-999804	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5*4-3)/2-1)$
-911643	$98-(7^6-5)/4*(32-1)$	-999855	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5-4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
-911839	$-98-(7^6-5)/4*(32-1)$	-999889	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5-4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$
-911980	$9-(8+(7^6-5)/4)*(32-1)$	-1000171	$9-8*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3/2-1)$
-914779	$(98+(7^6-5)/4)*(-32+1)$	-1000195	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5*4+3)/2-1)$
-916300	$(98+7/6)*5*(-43^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1000229	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5*4+3)/2+1)$
-919436	$-98*(7+6*5^4*(3/2+1))$	-1000263	$(-9-8)*((7^6+(5+4)*3)/2+1)$
-923769	$9*(8-7^6+5^4*(3+21))$	-1000297	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5*(4+3))/2-1)$
-926033	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4*3-21)$	-1000535	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5+4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$
-928119	$(9/(8-7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$	-1000586	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5+4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
-929935	$9+8*(7-6*5^4*(32-1))$	-1004454	$9*8/-7*((6/5^4/3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-936094	$98-(7^6-5^4)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1004615	$(-9-8)*((7^6+543)/2-1)$
-936290	$-98-(7^6-5^4)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1004649	$(-9-8)*((7^6+543)/2+1)$
-940077	$9*(8-7^6+(5^4+3)*21)$	-1015937	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^4*3)/2-1)$
-940221	$-9*(8+7^6-(5^4+3)*21)$	-1015971	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^4*3)/2+1)$
-941957	$9*(8*7*(6-5^4*3)+2)+1$	-1021839	$(-98+7)*(6*5^4*3-21)$
-941995	$9*(8*7*(6-5^4*3)-2)-1$	-1024923	$9^{\wedge}8/(7*-6)-5/(4+(3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$
-944064	$9*8*(76-(5^4+3)*21)$	-1025018	$9*(8-7^6+5^4*3*2)+1$
-945450	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^4*(3+21)))$	-1025020	$9*(8-7^6+5^4*3*2)-1$
-945936	$-9*8*(76+(5^4-3)*21)$	-1025088	$-9*8*76*(5^4/3-21)$
-946094	$98-(7^6+5^4)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1025162	$-9*(8+7^6-5^4*3*2)+1$
-946290	$-98-(7^6+5^4)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1025164	$-9*(8+7^6-5^4*3*2)-1$
-947879	$9*8*(-7*(6+5^4*3)+2)+1$	-1031183	$9-8*(7^6-5^4*(3-21))$
-947881	$9*8*(-7*(6+5^4*3)+2)-1$	-1031201	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4*(3-21))$
-948005	$9*(8*-7*(6+5^4*3)+2)+1$	-1035216	$(-98+7)*6*(5^4*3+21)$
-948007	$9*(8*-7*(6+5^4*3)+2)-1$	-1036323	$-9/(8*(7*6+5/4/3))^{\wedge}-2+1$
-948041	$-9*(8*7*(6+5^4*3)+2)+1$	-1036325	$-9/(8*(7*6+5/4/3))^{\wedge}-2-1$
-948043	$-9*(8*7*(6+5^4*3)+2)-1$	-1040375	$9-8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*(4-32^{\wedge}-1)$
-948167	$9*-8*(7*(6+5^4*3)+2)+1$	-1040393	$-9-8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*(4-32^{\wedge}-1)$
-948169	$9*-8*(7*(6+5^4*3)+2)-1$	-1041219	$-9*(87+6)*(5^4-3)*2-1$
-956351	$9-8*(7^6+5^4*3+21)$	-1041705	$9*(8-7^6+5^4*3+21)$
-957519	$9*(8-7^6-5^4*(3-21))$	-1041849	$-9*(8+7^6-5^4*3-21)$
-959887	$9+8*(7-6*(5^4*32-1))$	-1045133	$-9*(8*7+6)*(5^4*3-2)+1$
-959927	$9+8*(7-6*5^4*32+1)$	-1045135	$-9*(8*7+6)*(5^4*3-2)-1$
-959943	$9+8*(7-6*5^4*32-1)$	-1045467	$9*(87-6*5^4*(32-1))$
-959983	$9+8*(7-6*(5^4*32+1))$	-1045679	$9-8*(7^6+(5^4-3)*21)$
-960095	$9-8*(7+6*(5^4*32+1))$	-1045697	$-9-8*(7^6+(5^4-3)*21)$
-962899	$-98*((7^6+5)/4/3+21)$	-1046295	$-9*((87+6)*5^4+3)*2-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1046687	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21)$	-1101835	$98^*(7 - 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) - 21$
-1047033	$-9^*(87 + 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 - 1))$	-1102446	$-9 - ((8 + 76) * 5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21$
-1047365	$9^*(8 * 7 + 6) * (5^{\wedge}4 * -3 - 2) + 1$	-1102554	$9 - ((8 + 76) * 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21$
-1047367	$9^*(8 * 7 + 6) * (5^{\wedge}4 * -3 - 2) - 1$	-1103165	$-98^*(7 + 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) + 21$
-1047464	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 2) + 1$	-1103207	$-98^*(7 + 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) - 21$
-1047466	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 2) - 1$	-1106183	$9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 + 1))$
-1047572	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 2) + 1$	-1106201	$-9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 + 1))$
-1047574	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 2) - 1$	-1111154	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4) / 3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-1047716	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 2) + 1$	-1112967	$9^*(87 - 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 + 1))$
-1056269	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6) + 5^{\wedge}4 * (3 + 2 - 1)$	-1114533	$-9^*(87 + 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 + 1))$
-1056413	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6) + 5^{\wedge}4 * (3 + 2 - 1)$	-1115654	$9 + (8 / (7 - (65^{\wedge}4 - 3) / 2))^{\wedge} - 1$
-1056705	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 / 3 + 21)$	-1115672	$-9 + (8 / (7 - (65^{\wedge}4 - 3) / 2))^{\wedge} - 1$
-1056759	$9 - 8^{\wedge}(7 - 6 + 5) * (4 + 32^{\wedge} - 1)$	-1119663	$9 + 8^*(7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 32) - 1)$
-1056777	$9 - 8^{\wedge}(7 - 6 + 5) * (4 + 32^{\wedge} - 1)$	-1120271	$9 - 8^*7^*(6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 32 - 1)$
-1056849	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 / 3 - 21)$	-1120335	$9 - 8^*(7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 32) + 1)$
-1057083	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 / 3 - 21)$	-1120337	$-9 - 8^*(7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 32) - 1)$
-1057218	$(9 - 8^*7) * 6^*(5^{\wedge}4 * 3^2 - 1)$	-1120353	$-9 - 8^*(7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 32) + 1)$
-1057227	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 / 3 + 21)$	-1129047	$-9^*(8^*76^*(5^{\wedge}4 / 3 - 2) - 1)$
-1057547	$(9 - 8^*7) * (6 / 5^{\wedge} - 4 * 3^2 + 1)$	-1129065	$-9^*(8^*76^*(5^{\wedge}4 / 3 - 2) + 1)$
-1057782	$(9 - 8^*7) * 6^*(5^{\wedge}4 * 3^2 + 1)$	-1135704	$(9 - 8^*76) * (5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 21)$
-1058322	$9 + (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * 3) * (2 + 1)$	-1135954	$(9 / ((-8^{\wedge}7 + 6) * 5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge} - 1$
-1058388	$-9 + (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * 3) * (2 + 1)$	-1138767	$9 - 8^*(76^*(5^{\wedge}4 * 3 - 2) - 1)$
-1058503	$9 + 8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) + 321$	-1138783	$9 - 8^*(76^*(5^{\wedge}4 * 3 - 2) + 1)$
-1058521	$-9 + 8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) + 321$	-1138785	$-9 - 8^*(76^*(5^{\wedge}4 * 3 - 2) - 1)$
-1058537	$-9 - 8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) + 321$	-1138801	$-9 - 8^*(76^*(5^{\wedge}4 * 3 - 2) + 1)$
-1059145	$9 + 8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) - 321$	-1139687	$9 - 8^*76^*(5^{\wedge}4 * 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-1059161	$9 - 8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) - 321$	-1140295	$9 - 8^*76^*(5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-1059179	$-9 - 8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) - 321$	-1140313	$-9 - 8^*76^*(5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-1059294	$9 + (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * 3) * (2 + 1)$	-1141199	$9 - 8^*(76^*(5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 2) - 1)$
-1060455	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 / 3 + 21)$	-1141215	$9 - 8^*(76^*(5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 2) + 1)$
-1060599	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 / 3 - 21)$	-1141217	$-9 - 8^*(76^*(5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 2) - 1)$
-1060833	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 / 3 - 21)$	-1141233	$-9 - 8^*(76^*(5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 2) + 1)$
-1060977	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 / 3 + 21)$	-1146267	$9^*((8 - 76) * (5^{\wedge}4 * 3 - 2) + 1)$
-1061269	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6) - 5^{\wedge}4 * (3 + 2 - 1)$	-1146285	$9^*((8 - 76) * (5^{\wedge}4 * 3 - 2) - 1)$
-1061413	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6) - 5^{\wedge}4 * (3 + 2 - 1)$	-1147311	$9^*((8 - 76) * 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 21)$
-1068822	$-9^*(8 + 76 * 5^{\wedge}4 * (3 / 2 + 1))$	-1147689	$9^*((8 - 76) * 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 - 21)$
-1069964	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 2) + 1$	-1148715	$9^*((8 - 76) * (5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 2) + 1)$
-1069966	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 2) - 1$	-1148733	$9^*((8 - 76) * (5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 2) - 1)$
-1070072	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 2) + 1$	-1150935	$-9^*(8^*76^*(5^{\wedge}4 / 3 + 2) - 1)$
-1070074	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 2) - 1$	-1150953	$-9^*(8^*76^*(5^{\wedge}4 / 3 + 2) + 1)$
-1070108	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 2) + 1$	-1154655	$9 + 8^*7^*(6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 + 1))$
-1070110	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 2) - 1$	-1155327	$9 - 8^*7^*(6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 + 1))$
-1070216	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 2) + 1$	-1155345	$-9 - 8^*7^*(6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 + 1))$
-1070218	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 2) - 1$	-1159755	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 21)$
-1074528	$9 * 8^*(76 - 5^{\wedge}4 * (3 + 21))$	-1160019	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * (3 - 21))$
-1075833	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 - 21)$	-1160163	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * (3 - 21))$
-1075977	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 21)$	-1160352	$9^*(8 - 76) * (5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 21)$
-1077408	$-9^*87 * 6^*(5^{\wedge}4 / 3 + 21)$	-1165096	$(9 / 8 / (-7 - 6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge} - 1$
-1077704	$(-9 / (8 + (7^*6 - 5) * 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge} - 1$	-1169832	$(-9 - 8^*76) * (5^{\wedge}4 * 3 + 21)$
-1079226	$9^*(87 - 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 * 32 - 1)$	-1170142	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-1079271	$9^*(87 - 6 * (5^{\wedge}4 * 32 + 1))$	-1173913	$9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / 4 - 321)$
-1079919	$9^*(8 + 7 - 6 * (5^{\wedge}4 * 32 + 1))$	-1173931	$-9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / 4 - 321)$
-1080063	$-9^*(8 - 7 + 6 * (5^{\wedge}4 * 32 + 1))$	-1175282	$-9 - (8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}5) / (4 / 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-1080081	$-9^*(8 + 7 + 6 * (5^{\wedge}4 * 32 - 1))$	-1175284	$-9 - (8^{\wedge}7 - 6^{\wedge}5) / (4 / 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-1080189	$-9^*(8 + 7 + 6 * (5^{\wedge}4 * 32 + 1))$	-1175571	$9 - (8 + 7) * 6^*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21$
-1080729	$-9^*(87 + 6 * (5^{\wedge}4 * 32 - 1))$	-1175589	$-9 - (8 + 7) * 6^*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21$
-1080774	$-9^*(87 + 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 * 32 - 1)$	-1175852	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-1081599	$-9 / (8 * (76 + 54) / 3)^{\wedge} - 2 + 1$	-1175977	$9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / 4 - 321)$
-1081601	$-9 / (8 * (76 + 54) / 3)^{\wedge} - 2 - 1$	-1176048	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-1084655	$9 + 8^*7^*(6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 - 1))$	-1176160	$9 - 8^*7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / 4 + 321$
-1085327	$9 - 8^*7^*(6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 - 1))$	-1176178	$-9 - 8^*7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / 4 + 321$
-1085472	$-9^*(8 * (76 + 54) * (3 + 21))$	-1176251	$-9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / 4 - 32 + 1)$
-1092518	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3^2) + 1$	-1176382	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-1092662	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3^2) + 1$	-1176598	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-1092664	$-9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3^2) - 1$	-1176729	$9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / 4 + 32 - 1)$
-1096183	$9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 - 1))$	-1176802	$9 - 8^*7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / 4 - 321$
-1096201	$-9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * (32 - 1))$	-1176820	$-9 - 8^*7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / 4 - 321$
-1101175	$9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 32 - 1)$	-1176932	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-1101191	$9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 32 + 1)$	-1176985	$9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / 4 + 3 * 21)$
-1101193	$-9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 32 - 1)$	-1177003	$-9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / 4 + 3 * 21)$
-1101209	$-9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 32 + 1)$	-1177128	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-1101793	$98^*(7 - 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) + 21$	-1177461	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1177605	$-9*(8+7^6+(5^4+3)*21)$	-1285650	$9*(8/7+6)*(5^4*-32+1)$
-1179045	$(-98-7)*(6*5^4*3-21)$	-1286005	$-98*((7*6*5^4-3)/2-1)$
-1179049	$9-8*(7^6*5/4+321)$	-1286936	$-98*(7+6*5^4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$
-1179067	$-9-8*(7^6*5/4+321)$	-1287181	$-98*(7*(6*5^4+3)/2-1)$
-1180296	$9-(8+7)*(6*5^4-3)*21$	-1289280	$(-98*7+6)*(5^4*3+21)$
-1182186	$-9-(8+7)*(6*5^4+3)*21$	-1290317	$-98*(7*(6+5^4*3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1182642	$98-(7^6+5^4)*(3^2+1)$	-1291150	$98*(7+6-(5^4+3)*21)$
-1182838	$-98-(7^6+5^4)*(3^2+1)$	-1293405	$(-9-8*7*6)*(5^4*3*2-1)$
-1183455	$(-98-7)*(6*5^4*3+21)$	-1293698	$-98*(7+6+(5^4+3)*21)$
-1184030	$-9-(8+7+6^5)/(4/3)^2+1$	-1294012	$9*8-(7^6-5)*(4+3*2+1)$
-1184032	$-9-(8+7+6^5)/(4/3)^2-1$	-1294266	$-9*8-(7^6+5)^*(4*3-2+1)$
-1186911	$9-(8+7)*6*(5^4+3)*21$	-1296936	$-9*(8+7*6*(5^4*3+21))$
-1194480	$(-98-7)*6*(5^4*3+21)$	-1299825	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^4*(32+1)))$
-1207224	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*(5*(4-3^{\wedge}-2)+1)$	-1302831	$9*876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
-1211896	$(-9-8)*((7/(6-5^4*3))^{\wedge}-2-1)$	-1302841	$9*876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
-1211930	$(-9-8)*((7/(6-5^4*3))^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-1307212	$(-9/(8+7^6*5*4*(3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-1220319	$9*(-8+7*(6-5^4*(32-1)))$	-1308664	$9/(8-(76*5+4/3)^2)^{\wedge}-1$
-1220553	$9-((87+6)*5^4-3)*21$	-1308808	$-9/(8+(76*5+4/3)^2)^{\wedge}-1$
-1220571	$-9-((87+6)*5^4-3)*21$	-1309830	$9+876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
-1220679	$9-((87+6)*5^4+3)*21$	-1309840	$9+876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
-1221075	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^4*(32-1)))$	-1309848	$-9+876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
-1225923	$(9-8*7*6)*(5^4*3*2-1)$	-1309858	$-9+876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
-1226577	$(9-8*7*6)*(5^4*3*2+1)$	-1310157	$9*(8*7+6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
-1229991	$-9*(8-7/6)*5^4*32-1$	-1310167	$9*(8*7+6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
-1233288	$-9*(8+7^6+5^4*(32-1))$	-1310265	$9*(8+7*6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
-1238904	$-9*(8+7^6+5^4*32-1)$	-1310275	$9*(8+7*6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
-1238922	$-9*(8+7^6+5^4*32+1)$	-1310419	$-9*(8-7*6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
-1239929	$9-(8*7+6)*(5^4*32-1)$	-1310472	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
-1239956	$9*(8+7*(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^2+1)$	-1310482	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
-1239958	$9*(8+7*(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^2-1)$	-1310914	$-9*(8+7+6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
-1240053	$9-(8*7+6)*(5^4*32+1)$	-1310937	$9-8*7^6*(5/4+3/21)$
-1240100	$-9*(8-7*(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^2+1)$	-1310955	$-9-8*7^6*(5/4+3/21)$
-1240102	$-9*(8-7*(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^2-1)$	-1311021	$9*(8-7*6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
-1243108	$(-9-8)*((7+6)*5^4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1311165	$-9*(8+7*6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
-1243142	$(-9-8)*((7+6)*5^4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1311273	$-9*(8*7+6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
-1243917	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-1311283	$-9*(8*7+6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
-1244403	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-1311582	$9-876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
-1244538	$-9*(8+7^6+5^4*(32+1))$	-1311592	$9-876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
-1251666	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$	-1311600	$-9-876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
-1251676	$9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$	-1311610	$-9-876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
-1254799	$9-8*((7^6+5)*4/3-21)$	-1312032	$(-98*7-6)*(5^4*3+21)$
-1254817	$-9-8*((7^6+5)*4/3-21)$	-1318609	$-9*876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^2+1)$
-1255135	$9-8*((7^6+5)*4/3+21)$	-1323422	$9*(8-(7^6-5)/4*(3+2))+1$
-1256183	$9-8*(7^6+5^4*3*21)$	-1323424	$9*(8-(7^6-5)/4*(3+2))-1$
-1256201	$-9-8*(7^6+5^4*3*21)$	-1326255	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^4)/3*2-1)$
-1260387	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^4*32-1))$	-1326289	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^4)/3*2+1)$
-1260459	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^4*32)+1)$	-1333327	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5+4)/3*2-1)$
-1260513	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^4*32)+1)$	-1333395	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5)*4/3/2-1)$
-1265000	$(-9/((8+7)^{\wedge}6-5^4*3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	-1333429	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5)*4/3/2+1)$
-1266250	$(-9/((8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^4*3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	-1333565	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^4)/3*2-1)$
-1278802	$98*(7+6-(5^4-3)*21)$	-1337203	$(9+8)*7*(6*(5^4*-3+2)+1)$
-1280520	$-9*(8+7*6*(5^4*3-2-1))$	-1337305	$(-9-8)*7*6*(5^4*3-2)-1$
-1281195	$-9*(8+7*6*(5^4*3-2)-1)$	-1337339	$(-9-8)*7*6*(5^4*3-2)+1$
-1281213	$-9*(8+7*6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$	-1337441	$(9+8)*7*(6*(5^4*-3+2)-1)$
-1281350	$-98*(7+6+(5^4-3)*21)$	-1338300	$9-(8/7+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
-1281888	$-9*(8+7*6*(5^4*3-2+1))$	-1338699	$(-9-8)*7*6*5^4*3-2-1$
-1282085	$98*(7*(6-5^4*3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1338733	$(-9-8)*7*6*5^4*3-2+1$
-1282183	$98*(7*(6-5^4*3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1338767	$(9+8)*7*6*5^4*3-2+1$
-1282230	$-9*(8+7*6*(5^4*3-2^{\wedge}-1))$	-1338971	$(-9-8)*7*(6*5^4*3+2)-1$
-1282239	$9*(8-7*6*5^4*3+21)$	-1339005	$(-9-8)*7*(6*5^4*3+2)+1$
-1282383	$-9*(8+7*6*5^4*3-21)$	-1340059	$(9+8)*7*(-6*(5^4*3+2)+1)$
-1282617	$9*(8-7*6*5^4*3-21)$	-1340161	$(-9-8)*7*6*(5^4*3+2)-1$
-1282653	$-9*(8+(7*6*5^4+3)*(2+1))$	-1340195	$(-9-8)*7*6*(5^4*3+2)+1$
-1282761	$-9*(8+7*6*5^4*3+21)$	-1342206	$9/8*(7^6-5*4^{\wedge}3^2-1)$
-1282770	$9*(8-7*6*(5^4*3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	-1343799	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^2-1)$
-1282914	$-9*(8+7*6*(5^4*3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	-1343833	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^2+1)$
-1283256	$-9*(8+7*6*(5^4*3+2-1))$	-1352808	$98-(7^6-5)*(4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1283787	$9*(8-7*6*(5^4*3+2)+1)$	-1352834	$9*8-(7^6-5)*(4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1283931	$-9*(8+7*6*(5^4*3+2)-1)$	-1352949	$9*8-(7^6+5)*(4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1284480	$9*(8-7*6*(5^4*3+2+1))$	-1352978	$-9*8-(7^6-5)*(4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1284624	$-9*(8+7*6*(5^4*3+2+1))$	-1358439	$9-8*(7+6)*(5^4-3)*21$
-1285564	$98*(7-6*5^4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	-1358457	$-9-8*(7+6)*(5^4-3)*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1364487	$9 \cdot 8^* ((7+6)^*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$	-1499944	$(9+8)^* ((7^{\wedge}6-5)/-4^*3+2-1)$
-1364928	$9 \cdot 8^* (7+6)^*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$	-1499978	$(9+8)^* ((7^{\wedge}6-5)/-4^*3-2+1)$
-1365054	$9 \cdot (8^* (7+6)^*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$	-1500097	$(-9-8)^* ((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1365495	$9 \cdot 8^* ((7+6)^*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$	-1512557	$9^* (8-7^{\wedge}6^*5/(4+3)^*2)+1$
-1371543	$9 \cdot 8^* (7+6)^* (5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$	-1512559	$9^* (8-7^{\wedge}6^*5/(4+3)^*2)-1$
-1372550	$(9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*(4+3))/(2+1)$	-1512701	$-9^* (8+7^{\wedge}6^*5/(4+3)^*2)+1$
-1372556	$(-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*(4+3))/(2+1)$	-1512703	$-9^* (8+7^{\wedge}6^*5/(4+3)^*2)-1$
-1389528	$9^*8^* (76-5^{\wedge}4^*(32-1))$	-1520343	$98-(7-6/5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1404488	$(-9/8^*(7+6/5^{\wedge}-4/3)^{\wedge}-2)^{\wedge}-1$	-1520513	$-9^*8-(7-6/5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1410592	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^*321)$	-1528182	$9^*(8-(7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
-1411123	$9 \cdot 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3/2-1)$	-1528326	$-9^*(8+(7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
-1411157	$-9 \cdot 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3/2+1)$	-1534742	$9 \cdot 876^{\wedge} (-5+4+3)^*2+1$
-1411467	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4/3+21)$	-1534744	$9 \cdot 876^{\wedge} (-5+4+3)^*2-1$
-1411669	$98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4+3)+21$	-1534762	$-9 \cdot 876^{\wedge} (-5+4+3)^*2-1$
-1411907	$-98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4+3)-21$	-1542510	$(9/(-8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2))^{\wedge}-1$
-1412109	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4/3+21)$	-1568487	$9 \cdot 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4)/3-21)$
-1412419	$9 \cdot 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3/2-1)$	-1568505	$-9 \cdot 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4)/3-21)$
-1413144	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^*3^*21)$	-1568759	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+43)/(2+1)$
-1417427	$9^*(8-7^*6/5^{\wedge}-4^*3^*2)+1$	-1568821	$(9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3))/(2+1)$
-1417429	$9^*(8-7^*6/5^{\wedge}-4^*3^*2)-1$	-1568823	$9 \cdot 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4)/3+21)$
-1417571	$-9^*(8+7^*6^*5^{\wedge}4^*3^*2)+1$	-1568827	$(-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3))/(2+1)$
-1417573	$-9^*(8+7^*6^*5^{\wedge}4^*3^*2)-1$	-1568841	$-9 \cdot 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4)/3+21)$
-1419003	$-9^*((8+76)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*3+2)-1)$	-1569186	$-9^*((87+6)^*5^{\wedge}4^*3-21)$
-1427229	$(-9/(8^{\wedge}7^*6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$	-1569564	$-9^*((87+6)^*5^{\wedge}4^*3+21)$
-1428544	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5/(4+3)+2+1)$	-1572753	$9^*(8+7)-6^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1428570	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1572772	$98-(7-6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1428646	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5/(4+3)+2+1)$	-1572975	$-9^*(8+7)+6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1432255	$(-9-8^*7/6)/(5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2)^{\wedge}-1$	-1579751	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3/2)+1$
-1434456	$9^*8^*(76-5^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$	-1579753	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3/2)-1$
-1434519	$9^*(8^*(76-5^{\wedge}4^*32)+1)$	-1579895	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3/2)+1$
-1434600	$9^*8^*(76-5^{\wedge}4^*32-1)$	-1579897	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*3/2)-1$
-1439055	$9^*(8^*(7+6-5^{\wedge}4^*32)+1)$	-1584963	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)^*43-21)$
-1439073	$9^*(8^*(7+6-5^{\wedge}4^*32)-1)$	-1585341	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)^*43+21)$
-1439907	$9^*(8^*(7/6-5^{\wedge}4^*32)+1)$	-1586203	$(9-8^*7)^*(6^*5^{\wedge}4/3^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-1440075	$-9^*(8^*(7/6+5^{\wedge}4^*32)-1)$	-1586297	$(9-8^*7)^*(6^*5^{\wedge}4/3^{\wedge}+2+1)$
-1440093	$-9^*(8^*(7/6+5^{\wedge}4^*32)+1)$	-1586952	$-9^*(87+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*3+21)$
-1440927	$-9^*(8^*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4^*32)-1)$	-1588067	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*3/2)+1$
-1441041	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4/32-1)$	-1588069	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*3/2)-1$
-1441237	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4/32+1)$	-1588121	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*3^*2)+1$
-1445400	$-9^*8^*(76+5^{\wedge}4^*32-1)$	-1588123	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*3^*2)-1$
-1445463	$-9^*(8^*(76+5^{\wedge}4^*32)-1)$	-1588204	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^*3/2)-1$
-1445481	$-9^*(8^*(76+5^{\wedge}4^*32)+1)$	-1588319	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^*3/2)+1$
-1445544	$-9^*8^*(76+5^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$	-1588400	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)/4^*3^*2)+1$
-1461852	$9^*(87^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^*3+2)+1)$	-1588402	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)/4^*3^*2)-1$
-1463400	$9^*(87^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)+2+1)$	-1588454	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*3/2)+1$
-1463406	$9^*87^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)+21$	-1588456	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*3/2)-1$
-1463418	$9^*(87^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)+2-1)$	-1596626	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3/2)+1$
-1463436	$9^*(87^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)-2+1)$	-1596628	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3/2)-1$
-1463448	$9^*87^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)-21$	-1596770	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3/2)+1$
-1463454	$9^*(87^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)-2-1)$	-1596772	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3/2)-1$
-1465002	$9^*(87^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^*3-2)-1)$	-1606914	$-9/8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1467594	$9+87^*(6-5^{\wedge}4^*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-1618848	$-9^*876^*(5^{\wedge}4/3-2-1)$
-1468638	$9 \cdot 87^*(6+5^{\wedge}4^*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-1626723	$-9^*(876^*(5^{\wedge}4/3-2)-1)$
-1470452	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1626731	$-9^*876^*(5^{\wedge}4/3-2)+1$
-1470478	$9^*8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1626732	$-9^*876^*(5^{\wedge}4/3-2)^{\wedge}1$
-1470577	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1626733	$-9^*876^*(5^{\wedge}4/3-2)-1$
-1470603	$9^*8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1626741	$-9^*(876^*(5^{\wedge}4/3-2)+1)$
-1470622	$-9^*8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1638558	$-9^*876^*(5^{\wedge}4/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1470747	$-9^*8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-1642071	$-9 \cdot 876^*(5^{\wedge}4^*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1472634	$-9^*(87^*(6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)-21)$	-1642929	$9 \cdot 876^*(5^{\wedge}4^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1472796	$-9^*(87^*(6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)-2-1)$	-1642947	$-9 \cdot 876^*(5^{\wedge}4^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1472802	$-9^*87^*(6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)+21$	-1646442	$-9^*876^*(5^{\wedge}4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-1472844	$-9^*87^*(6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)-21$	-1646909	$9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5/4-3)+21)$
-1473012	$-9^*(87^*(6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)+21)$	-1647245	$9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5/4-3)-21)$
-1479528	$9^*8^*(76-5^{\wedge}4^*(32+1))$	-1647263	$-9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5/4-3)-21)$
-1490188	$(98+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-43))/(2+1)$	-1649634	$98^*(7^*6-5^{\wedge}4^*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-1490227	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-43))/(2+1)$	-1655808	$(-98-7^*6/5^{\wedge}-4^*3)^*21$
-1490472	$-9^*8^*(76+5^{\wedge}4^*(32+1))$	-1657866	$-98^*(7^*6+5^{\wedge}4^*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-1495944	$(-9^*87-6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*3+21)$	-1658259	$-9^*(876^*(5^{\wedge}4/3+2)-1)$
-1496178	$9^*(8-76^*5^{\wedge}4^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	-1658267	$-9^*876^*(5^{\wedge}4/3+2)+1$
-1496322	$-9^*(8+76^*5^{\wedge}4^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	-1658268	$-9^*876^*(5^{\wedge}4/3+2)^{\wedge}1$
-1499910	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/-4^*3+2+1)$	-1658269	$-9^*876^*(5^{\wedge}4/3+2)-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1658277	$-9*(876*(5^4/3+2)+1)$	-1853052	$9-(8+(7^6-5)/4^3)*21$
-1666152	$-9*876*(5^4/3+2+1)$	-1853388	$9-(8+(7^6-5)/4)^3*21$
-1686198	$(98-(7^6-5)*43)/(2+1)$	-1853406	$-9-(8+(7^6-5)/4)^3*21$
-1686219	$9+(8-(7^6-5)*43)/(2+1)$	-1854951	$(98+(7^6-5)/4^3)^*-21$
-1686237	$-9+(8-(7^6-5)*43)/(2+1)$	-1855516	$(-9-8)*((7+6)^5-4^3*2-1)$
-1686276	$98-(7^6+5)*43/(2+1)$	-1855550	$(-9-8)*((7+6)^5-4^3*2+1)$
-1686472	$-98-(7^6+5)*43/(2+1)$	-1860497	$-9*((8*7^6+5)*4/3)^2-1$
-1703962	$(-9+(8+7)/6)^*(5+4^3*2-1)$	-1872491	$9-8*7/6/5^4-4*321$
-1710099	$-9*(8*(76*5^4+3)/2-1)$	-1873697	$-9-8*((7^6-543)^2-1)$
-1712325	$9+8*((6-5-4)^3*2+1)$	-1878943	$9-8*((7^6-5^4*43)^2+1)$
-1712499	$9+8*((6-5-4)^3*2-1)$	-1879791	$9-8*((7^6-54^3)^2+1)$
-1713158	$(-9-8)*(7^6-5^4*3^3*(2+1))$	-1881471	$9-8*((7^6-54-3)^2+1)$
-1756070	$(9-(8*7)^{-(6+5+4)})*(3^2+1)$	-1881567	$9-8*((7^6-54+3)^2+1)$
-1756250	$(-9-(8*7)^{-(6+5+4)})*(3^2+1)$	-1881615	$9-8*((7^6-5-43)^2+1)$
-1762677	$(98-7^6*5/(4+3))^*21$	-1881775	$9-8*((7^6+5-43)^2+1)$
-1766793	$(98+7^6*5/(4+3))^*-21$	-1881974	$(9-8*(7^6/5-4))^*(3^2+1)$
-1773559	$9-8^{-(7+6+5)}*(432+1)$	-1882154	$(-9-8*(7^6/5-4))^*(3^2+1)$
-1773577	$-9-8^{-(7+6+5)}*(432+1)$	-1882207	$9+8*(7^6*(5-4-3)+21)$
-1780471	$98+7*(6^5-4^3*2+1)$	-1882233	$9*(8-(7^6-5)^*(4/3)^2)-1$
-1780485	$98+7*(6^5-4^3*2-1)$	-1882535	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)^*(4/3)^2)+1$
-1780667	$-98+7*(6^5-4^3*2+1)$	-1882614	$(9-8*(7^6/5+4))^*(3^2+1)$
-1780681	$-98+7*(6^5-4^3*2-1)$	-1882671	$9-8*((7^6+54/3)^2+1)$
-1792742	$(98-7^6*5^4*3)/21$	-1882794	$(-9-8*(7^6/5+4))^*(3^2+1)$
-1794296	$(9/8-7*(6-543)^{-2})^{-1}$	-1882991	$9-8*((7^6-5+43)^2+1)$
-1798919	$9*(8*(7+6^5)-4^3*2)+1$	-1883151	$9-8*((7^6+5+43)^2+1)$
-1798921	$-9*(8*(7+6^5)-4^3*2)-1$	-1883199	$9-8*((7^6+54-3)^2+1)$
-1799901	$9-(8+7)*6*(5^4*32-1)$	-1883295	$9-8*((7^6+54+3)^2+1)$
-1799927	$-9*(8*(7-6^5)+4^3*2)+1$	-1884975	$9-8*((7^6+54^3)^2+1)$
-1799929	$-9*(8*(7-6^5)+4^3*2)-1$	-1885823	$9-8*((7^6+5^4*3)^2+1)$
-1799976	$9-(8+7)*6*(5^4*32-1)$	-1889335	$98-7*(6^5+4^3*2-1)$
-1800006	$9-(8+7)*6*(5^4*32+1)$	-1889349	$98-7*(6^5+4^3*2+1)$
-1800081	$9-(8+7)*6*(5^4*32+1)$	-1891071	$9-8*((7^6+543)^2+1)$
-1800090	$(-9-87+6)*(5^4*32+1)$	-1891073	$-9-8*((7^6+543)^2-1)$
-1800099	$-9-(8+7)*6*(5^4*32+1)$	-1893783	$(-9-8)*(7^6-5^4*(3^2+1))$
-1804689	$9*(8*(7+6)-5^4*321)$	-1904425	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*3^2-1)$
-1804815	$9*((8+7)*6-5^4*321)$	-1915033	$(-9-8)*(7^6-5^4*(3^2-1))$
-1805067	$9*(8*7+6-5^4*321)$	-1915926	$9*(8+7^6*(5-43)/21)$
-1805541	$9*(8*7/6-5^4*321)$	-1921829	$-98*((7^6+5^4)/3/2-1)$
-1805571	$9/(8-7)*(6-5^4*321)$	-1927192	$(9-(8*7^6-5)^4*3)/21$
-1805679	$-9*(8-7)*(6+5^4*321)$	-1927285	$(-9-8*(7^6+5)^4*3)/21$
-1805709	$-9*(8*7/6+5^4*321)$	-1929522	$98*(-7+(6-5-4)^3*2+1)$
-1806183	$-9*(8*7+6+5^4*321)$	-1929718	$98*(-7+(6-5-4)^3*2-1)$
-1806435	$-9*((8+7)*6+5^4*321)$	-1936266	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*3^2+1)$
-1806561	$-9*(8*(7+6)+5^4*321)$	-1936300	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*3^2-1)$
-1815128	$(98-7^6*5^4)/(3+2^2-1)$	-1943757	$9^8((8+7)/6)*((-5^4)^3+2-1)$
-1815184	$(98+7^6*5^4)/(-3-2^2-1)$	-1944243	$9^8((8+7)/6)*((-5^4)^3-2+1)$
-1834448	$98+7*(65-4^3*2+1)$	-1957533	$(-9-8)*(7^6-5^4*(3+2-1))$
-1834454	$98+7*(65-4^3*2)+1$	-1968005	$(-9-8)*(7^6-(5^4+3)^*(2+1))$
-1834456	$98+7*(65-4^3*2)-1$	-1968107	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*3+2+1)$
-1834462	$98+7*(65-4^3*2-1)$	-1968141	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*3+2-1)$
-1834644	$-98+7*(65-4^3*2+1)$	-1968175	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*3-2+1)$
-1834650	$-98+7*(65-4^3*2)+1$	-1968209	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*3-2-1)$
-1834652	$-98+7*(65-4^3*2)-1$	-1968311	$(-9-8)*(7^6-(5^4-3)^*(2+1))$
-1834658	$-98+7*(65-4^3*2-1)$	-1973609	$9*(8-(7^6-(5^4)^3)^2)+1$
-1834693	$98+7*(6*5-4^3*2+1)$	-1973611	$9*(8-(7^6-(5^4)^3)^2)-1$
-1834707	$98+7*(6*5-4^3*2-1)$	-1973753	$-9*(8+(7^6-(5^4)^3)^2)+1$
-1834826	$98+7*(6+5-4^3*2+1)$	-1973755	$-9*(8+(7^6-(5^4)^3)^2)-1$
-1834840	$98+7*(6+5-4^3*2-1)$	-1978664	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*3)^2+1$
-1835127	$98-7*(6*5+4^3*2+1)$	-1978698	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*3)^2-1$
-1835358	$98-7*(65+4^3*2-1)$	-1978868	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*3)^2+1$
-1835364	$98-7*(65+4^3*2)+1$	-1978902	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*3)^2-1$
-1835366	$98-7*(65+4^3*2)-1$	-1991703	$(98-7^6/5)^*(4^3+21)$
-1835372	$98-7*(65+4^3*2+1)$	-1994712	$(9+8)*(-7^6+5^4*3)/2-1$
-1835554	$-98-7*(65+4^3*2-1)$	-1999344	$9+(8-7^6/5)^*(43^2-1)$
-1835560	$-98-7*(65+4^3*2)+1$	-2000535	$9-8*((7/(6/54))^3+21)$
-1835562	$-98-7*(65+4^3*2)-1$	-2000553	$-9-8*((7/(6/54))^3+21)$
-1850835	$(98-(7^6-5)/4^3)^*21$	-2000704	$9-(8+7^6/5)^*(4^3+21)$
-1852380	$9+(8-(7^6-5)/4)^3*21$	-2000722	$-9-(8+7^6/5)^*(4^3+21)$
-1852716	$9+(8-(7^6-5)/4^3)^*21$	-2005354	$(-9-8)*(7^6+5^4*3)/2-1$
-1852734	$-9+(8-(7^6-5)/4^3)^*21$	-2008363	$(98+7^6/5)^*(-4^3*2+1)$
-1852795	$98-(7^6-5)/4^3*21$	-2008434	$(-9+87/65)^*(4^3*2+1)$
-1852991	$-98-(7^6-5)/4^3*21$	-2012049	$9*87*((-6^5+4)/3+21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2014137	$9*8^7*((6^5+4)/-3+21)$	-2107981	$-9*(8+(7^6-543)*2)-1$
-2016813	$(9-8*7^6*5/(4+3))*(2+1)$	-2107989	$-9*(8+(7^6-543)*2+1)$
-2016867	$(-9-8*7^6*5/(4+3))*(2+1)$	-2111849	$9*(8-(7^6-5*4^3)*2)+1$
-2017477	$98*(7/6-5^4)^*(32+1)$	-2111851	$9*(8-(7^6-5*4^3)*2)-1$
-2021164	$(-9-8)*(7^6+(5^4-3)*2-1)$	-2111993	$-9*(8+(7^6-5*4^3)*2)+1$
-2021198	$(-9-8)*(7^6+(5^4-3)*2+1)$	-2111995	$-9*(8+(7^6-5*4^3)*2)-1$
-2021368	$(-9-8)*(7^6+(5^4+3)*2-1)$	-2113859	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4/3)*2)+1$
-2021402	$(-9-8)*(7^6+(5^4+3)*2+1)$	-2113861	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4/3)*2)-1$
-2025023	$-98*(7/6+5^4)^*(32+1)$	-2113875	$-9*(8+(7^6-5*4^3)*2-1)$
-2031755	$(-9-8)*(7^6+(5^4-3)*(2+1))$	-2113893	$-9*(8+(7^6-5*4^3)*2+1)$
-2031857	$(-9-8)*(7^6+5^4*3-2-1)$	-2114003	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4/3)*2)+1$
-2031891	$(-9-8)*(7^6+5^4*3-2+1)$	-2114005	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4/3)*2)-1$
-2031925	$(-9-8)*(7^6+5^4*3+2-1)$	-2114829	$-9*(8+(7^6-5*4^3)*2-1)$
-2031959	$(-9-8)*(7^6+5^4*3+2+1)$	-2114883	$-9*(8*(7^6+5)/4-321)$
-2032061	$(-9-8)*(7^6+(5^4+3)*(2+1))$	-2115279	$9*(8*((7^6-5)/-4+32)+1)$
-2035155	$(-9-8)*((7^6-6+5+4)+3)^2-1$	-2116529	$9*(8-(7^6-5*4^3)*2)+1$
-2042533	$(-9-8)*(7^6+5^4*(3+2-1))$	-2116531	$9*(8-(7^6-5*4^3)*2)-1$
-2044935	$9*8^7*((-6^5+4)/3-21)$	-2116547	$9*(8-(7^6+5-4^3)*2)+1$
-2063766	$(-9-8)*(7^6+5^4*3^2-1)$	-2116549	$9*(8-(7^6+5-4^3)*2)-1$
-2063800	$(-9-8)*(7^6+5^4*3^2+1)$	-2116709	$9-8+(7^6-54)^*(3-21)$
-2079887	$9-8*(7+6)*(5^4*32-1)$	-2116711	$-9+8+(7^6-54)^*(3-21)$
-2080095	$9+8*(7+6)*(5^4*32+1)$	-2116719	$-9*(8+(7^6-5-4^3)*2-1)$
-2080113	$-9-8*(7+6)*(5^4*32+1)$	-2116881	$-9*(8+(7^6-5-4^3)*2-1)$
-2083859	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4*3)*2)+1$	-2116979	$9*(8-(7^6-5*(4+3))*2)+1$
-2083861	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4*3)*2)-1$	-2116981	$9*(8-(7^6-5*(4+3))*2)-1$
-2084003	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4*3)*2)+1$	-2117079	$-9*(8+(7^6+5-4^3)*2+1)$
-2084005	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4*3)*2)-1$	-2117267	$-9*(8+(7^6-(5+4)*3)*2)+1$
-2085033	$(-9-8)*(7^6+5^4*(3^2-1))$	-2117269	$-9*(8+(7^6-(5+4)*3)*2)-1$
-2091015	$9+8*(765-4^3*2+1)$	-2117422	$98+(7^6-5-4)^*(3-21)$
-2091022	$9+8*(765-4^3*2)+1$	-2117495	$9*(8-(7^6-5-4^3)*2)+1$
-2091024	$9+8*(765-4^3*2)-1$	-2117497	$9*(8-(7^6-5-4^3)*2)-1$
-2091031	$9+8*(765-4^3*2-1)$	-2117644	$9+8-7^6*54/3+21$
-2091033	$-9+8*(765-4^3*2+1)$	-2117720	$-9-8-7^6*54/3-21$
-2091040	$-9+8*(765-4^3*2)+1$	-2117867	$-9*(8+(7^6+5+4/3)*2)+1$
-2091042	$-9+8*(765-4^3*2)-1$	-2117869	$-9*(8+(7^6+5+4/3)*2)-1$
-2091049	$-9+8*(765-4^3*2-1)$	-2117875	$-9*(8+(7^6+5*4/3)*2)-1$
-2093495	$9+8*(7*65-4^3*2+1)$	-2117942	$-98+(7^6+5+4)^*(3-21)$
-2093511	$9+8*(7*65-4^3*2-1)$	-2118095	$9*(8-(7^6+(5+4)*3)*2)+1$
-2093529	$-9+8*(7*65-4^3*2-1)$	-2118097	$9*(8-(7^6+(5+4)*3)*2)-1$
-2094095	$9+8*(76*5-4^3*2+1)$	-2118383	$-9*(8+(7^6+5*(4+3))*2)+1$
-2094111	$9+8*(76*5-4^3*2-1)$	-2118385	$-9*(8+(7^6+5*(4+3))*2)-1$
-2094129	$-9+8*(76*5-4^3*2-1)$	-2118653	$9-8+(7^6+54)^*(3-21)$
-2094480	$-9*8*((7^6-5)/4-321)$	-2118655	$-9+8+(7^6+54)^*(3-21)$
-2095675	$(-9-8)*(7^6+5^4*3^2+1)$	-2118815	$-9*(8+(7^6-5+4^3)*2)+1$
-2096583	$9+8*(76-5-4^3*2-1)$	-2118817	$-9*(8+(7^6-5+4^3)*2)-1$
-2097703	$9-8*(76-5+4^3*2-1)$	-2118833	$-9*(8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2)+1$
-2100175	$9-8*(76*5+4^3*2-1)$	-2118835	$-9*(8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2)-1$
-2100191	$9-8*(76*5+4^3*2+1)$	-2119887	$9*(8*((7^6-5)/-4-32)+1)$
-2100775	$9-8*(7*65+4^3*2-1)$	-2119905	$9*(8*((7^6-5)/-4-32)-1)$
-2100791	$9-8*(7*65+4^3*2+1)$	-2120067	$9*(8*((7^6+5)/-4-32)+1)$
-2103255	$9-8*(765+4^3*2-1)$	-2120661	$-9*(8*(7^6+5)/4+321)$
-2103262	$9-8*(765+4^3*2)+1$	-2120679	$-9*(8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2+1)$
-2103264	$9-8*(765+4^3*2)-1$	-2121359	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4/3)*2)+1$
-2103271	$9-8*(765+4^3*2+1)$	-2121361	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4/3)*2)-1$
-2103273	$-9-8*(765+4^3*2-1)$	-2121503	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4/3)*2)+1$
-2103280	$-9-8*(765+4^3*2)+1$	-2121505	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4/3)*2)-1$
-2103282	$-9-8*(765+4^3*2)-1$	-2121615	$-9*(8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2-1)$
-2103289	$-9-8*(765+4^3*2+1)$	-2121633	$-9*(8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2+1)$
-2106305	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4-3)*2)+1$	-2123369	$9*(8-(7^6+5*4^3)*2)+1$
-2106307	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4-3)*2)-1$	-2123371	$9*(8-(7^6+5*4^3)*2)-1$
-2106334	$98+(7^6-5^4)^*(3-21)$	-2123513	$-9*(8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2)+1$
-2106451	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4-3)*2)-1$	-2123515	$-9*(8+(7^6+5*4^3)*2)-1$
-2106530	$-98+(7^6-5^4)^*(3-21)$	-2124855	$9*(8+(7-6/5^4-4^3)*21)$
-2106557	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4+3)*2)+1$	-2125382	$9-(8+7/65)^*(4^3*2+1)$
-2106559	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4+3)*2)-1$	-2125400	$-9-(8+7/65)^*(4^3*2+1)$
-2107827	$9*(8-(7^6-543)*2+1)$	-2127033	$-9*(87+6/5^4-4^3*21)$
-2107836	$9*(8-(7^6-543)*2)^1$	-2127375	$9*(8-(7^6+543)*2+1)$
-2107837	$9*(8-(7^6-543)*2)-1$	-2127385	$9*(8-(7^6+543)*2)-1$
-2107845	$9*(8-(7^6-543)*2-1)$	-2127393	$9*(8-(7^6+543)*2-1)$
-2107971	$-9*(8+(7^6-543)*2-1)$	-2127501	$9*(8-(7+6/5^4-4^3)*21)$
-2107979	$-9*(8+(7^6-543)*2)+1$	-2127519	$-9*(8+(7^6+543)*2-1)$
-2107980	$-9*(8+(7^6-543)*2)^1$	-2127527	$-9*(8+(7^6+543)*2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2127528	$-9*(8+(7^6+543)*2)*1$	-2308410	$9*(87*65-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2127529	$-9*(8+(7^6+543)*2)-1$	-2313960	$-98+(7^6+5)*4/3-21$
-2127537	$-9*(8+(7^6+543)*2+1)$	-2319867	$9*(876*5-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2127645	$-9*(8+(7+6/5^4-4^3)*21)$	-2319875	$9*(876*5-4^4*3^2)+1$
-2128805	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4-3)*2)+1$	-2319877	$9*(876*5-4^4*3^2)-1$
-2128807	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4-3)*2)-1$	-2319885	$9*(876*5-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2128834	$98+(7^6+5^4)*(3-21)$	-2336075	$98-7^6*(5*4-3/21)$
-2128913	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4+3)*2)+1$	-2336271	$-98-7^6*(5*4-3/21)$
-2128951	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4-3)*2)-1$	-2339811	$9*(8-(7+6)*(5^4*3^2-1))$
-2129030	$-98+(7^6+5^4)*(3-21)$	-2339955	$-9*(8+(7+6)*(5^4*3^2-1))$
-2129057	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4+3)*2)+1$	-2340045	$9*(8-(7+6)*(5^4*3^2+1))$
-2129059	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4+3)*2)-1$	-2340189	$-9*(8+(7+6)*(5^4*3^2+1))$
-2140704	$-9*8*((7^6-5)/4+321)$	-2342260	$(9+8)*(7*(6-5-4)^4*3^2+1)$
-2140884	$-9*8*((7^6+5)/4+321)$	-2342294	$(9+8)*(7*(6-5-4)^4*3^2-1)$
-2149491	$98-(7+6/5)*(4^3*2+1)$	-2343609	$9*(8+7)-6*(5^4*(3/2)-1)$
-2149517	$9*8-(7+6/5)*(4^3*2+1)$	-2343621	$9*(8+7)-6*(5^4*(3/2)+1)$
-2149661	$-9*8-(7+6/5)*(4^3*2+1)$	-2343879	$-9*(8+7)-6*(5^4*(3/2)-1)$
-2149687	$-98+(7+6/5)*(4^3*2+1)$	-2343891	$-9*(8+7)-6*(5^4*(3/2)+1)$
-2151361	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4*3)*2)-1$	-2344175	$9*(8*7*6*5-4^4*3^2)+1$
-2151503	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4*3)*2)+1$	-2344177	$9*(8*7*6*5-4^4*3^2)-1$
-2151505	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4*3)*2)-1$	-2350512	$9*((8+7)*65-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2196100	$(9-(8*7^6-5)*(4+3))/(2+1)$	-2350674	$9*(87*(6+5)-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2196106	$(9+(8/7^6-6-5)*(4+3))/(-2-1)$	-2350692	$9*(87*(6+5)-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2196194	$-98*((7^6+5)^4-3)/21$	-2351358	$9*(876+5-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2196205	$(9-8*(7^6+5)*(4+3))/(2+1)$	-2351376	$9*(876+5-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2196211	$(-9-8*(7^6+5)*(4+3))/(2+1)$	-2351448	$9*(876-5-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2196222	$-98*((7^6+5)^4+3)/21$	-2351466	$9*(876-5-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2201920	$98-7*6/5*(4^3*2+1)$	-2351891	$9-8*(7^6-5^4)*(3/2+1)$
-2235138	$98-(7^6-5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$	-2352330	$9*(8+765-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2235164	$9*8-(7^6-5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$	-2352348	$9*(8+765-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2235308	$9*-8-(7^6-5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$	-2352474	$-9*(8-765+4^4*3^2-1)$
-2235354	$9*8-(7^6+5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$	-2352492	$-9*(8-765+4^4*3^2+1)$
-2235498	$9*-8-(7^6+5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$	-2353473	$9*(8*(76+5)-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2246937	$(9-8*7/6^5)/((4/3)^2-1)$	-2353770	$9*(8*76+5-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2250162	$9*(8-(7/(6/54))^4+21)$	-2353788	$9*(8*76+5-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2250306	$-9*(8+(7/(6/54))^4-21)$	-2353860	$9*(8*76-5-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2250330	$9*(8-(7/(6/54))^4)+21$	-2353878	$9*(8*76-5-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2250372	$9*(8-(7/(6/54))^4)-21$	-2354051	$9-8*(7^6+5^4)*(3/2+1)$
-2250474	$-9*(8+(7/(6/54))^4)+21$	-2354103	$9*(8*(7+65)-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2250516	$-9*(8+(7/(6/54))^4)-21$	-2354121	$9*(8*(7+65)-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2250540	$9*(8-(7/(6/54))^4)-21$	-2354175	$9*(8*(76-5)-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2250684	$-9*(8+(7/(6/54))^4)+21$	-2354193	$9*(8*(76-5)-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2261609	$9*(8-(7^6+(5*4)^3)*2)+1$	-2354544	$9*(87*6+5-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2261611	$9*(8-(7^6+(5*4)^3)*2)-1$	-2354562	$9*(87*6+5-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2261753	$-9*(8+(7^6+(5*4)^3)*2)+1$	-2354634	$9*(87*6-5-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2261755	$-9*(8+(7^6+(5*4)^3)*2)-1$	-2354652	$9*(87*6-5-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2268567	$(98-7^6*5)*(4-3/21)$	-2355102	$9*((87+6)*5-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2268847	$98-7^6*5*(4-3/21)$	-2355264	$-9*(8-7*65+4^4*3^2-1)$
-2269043	$-98-7^6*5*(4-3/21)$	-2355282	$-9*(8-7*65+4^4*3^2+1)$
-2269323	$(98+7^6*5)*(4+3/21)$	-2355507	$9*((8+76)*5-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2286781	$-98*7/6*(5^4*3^2+1)$	-2355525	$9*((8+76)*5-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2286908	$(-9-8)*(7^6+5^4*3^3*(2+1))$	-2355642	$9*((87-6)*5-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2288520	$9*(87+6^4*5-4^4*3^2+1)$	-2355660	$9*((87-6)*5-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2288538	$9*(87+6^4*5-4^4*3^2-1)$	-2355911	$9*(8*(7*6+5)-4^4*3^2)+1$
-2290086	$-9*(87-6^4*5+4^4*3^2-1)$	-2355913	$9*(8*(7*6+5)-4^4*3^2)-1$
-2290104	$-9*(87-6^4*5+4^4*3^2+1)$	-2355939	$-9*(8-76*5+4^4*3^2-1)$
-2302101	$(9-876^4(-5+4+3))*(2+1)$	-2355957	$-9*(8-76*5+4^4*3^2+1)$
-2302155	$(9+876^4(-5+4+3))*(-2-1)$	-2356633	$9*(8*(7*6-5)-4^4*3^2)-1$
-2302531	$98-(7^6-(5*4)^3)*21$	-2357335	$9*(8+7*6*5-4^4*3^2)-1$
-2302630	$-9+8-(7^6-(5*4)^3)*21$	-2357477	$-9*(8-7*6*5+4^4*3^2)+1$
-2302646	$-9-8-(7^6-(5*4)^3)*21$	-2357479	$-9*(8-7*6*5+4^4*3^2)-1$
-2302727	$-98-(7^6-(5*4)^3)*21$	-2357767	$9*((-8+7*6)*5-4^4*3^2)-1$
-2304207	$9*(8*765-4^4*3^2+1)$	-2357919	$9*(87+65-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2304215	$9*(8*765-4^4*3^2)+1$	-2357927	$9*(87+65-4^4*3^2)+1$
-2304217	$9*(8*765-4^4*3^2)-1$	-2357929	$9*(87+65-4^4*3^2)-1$
-2304225	$9*(8*765-4^4*3^2-1)$	-2357937	$9*(87+65-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2305548	$98*(7^6/-5+4-(3+2)^4-1)$	-2358198	$9*(8*7+65-4^4*3^2+1)$
-2305891	$98*(7^6/-5+(4/3+2)^4-1)$	-2358216	$9*(8*7+65-4^4*3^2-1)$
-2306332	$98*(7^6/-5-4-(3+2)^4-1)$	-2358674	$-9*(8-7*(6+5)+4^4*3^2)+1$
-2308392	$9*(87*65-4^4*3^2+1)$	-2358676	$-9*(8-7*(6+5)+4^4*3^2)-1$
-2308400	$9*(87*65-4^4*3^2)+1$	-2358837	$-9*(8+7-65+4^4*3^2-1)$
-2308402	$9*(87*65-4^4*3^2)-1$	-2358853	$9*(8*(7/6+5)-4^4*3^2)-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2359019	$-9*(8*(7/6-5)+4^3)^2+1$	-2398715	$-9*(876*5+4^3)^2+1$
-2359021	$-9*(8*(7/6-5)+4^3)^2-1$	-2398717	$-9*(876*5+4^3)^2-1$
-2359072	$9*((-8+7+6)*5-4^3)^2-1$	-2398725	$-9*(876*5+4^3)^2+1$
-2359097	$9*(87-65-4^3)^2+1$	-2410182	$-9*(87*65+4^3)^2-1$
-2359099	$9*(87-65-4^3)^2-1$	-2410190	$-9*(87*65+4^3)^2+1$
-2359493	$-9*(87-65+4^3)^2+1$	-2410192	$-9*(87*65+4^3)^2-1$
-2359495	$-9*(87-65+4^3)^2-1$	-2410200	$-9*(87*65+4^3)^2+1$
-2359612	$-9*((8-7+6)*5+4^3)^2-1$	-2411604	$98-(7^6-5)*(43/2-1)$
-2359655	$-9*(8*(7-6)*5+4^3)^2+1$	-2412005	$-98-(7^6+5)*(43/2-1)$
-2359657	$-9*(8*(7-6)*5+4^3)^2-1$	-2414367	$-9*(8*765+4^3)^2-1$
-2359739	$-9*(8*(7/6+5)+4^3)^2+1$	-2414375	$-9*(8*765+4^3)^2+1$
-2359741	$-9*(8*(7/6+5)+4^3)^2-1$	-2414377	$-9*(8*765+4^3)^2-1$
-2359971	$-9*(87-6-5+4^3)^2-1$	-2414385	$-9*(8*765+4^3)^2+1$
-2359989	$-9*(87-6-5+4^3)^2+1$	-2428506	$9*(87-6^5-4^3)^2-1$
-2359998	$-9*(8+76-5+4^3)^2-1$	-2431077	$9+(8-7^6+5^4*3)*21$
-2360025	$-9*(8+7+65+4^3)^2+1$	-2431095	$-9+(8-7^6+5^4*3)*21$
-2360106	$-9*(8+76+5+4^3)^2+1$	-2431156	$98-(7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-2360169	$-9*(8+76+5+4^3)^2-1$	-2431352	$-98-(7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-2360278	$-9*(8*(7+6)+5+4^3)^2-1$	-2431413	$9-(8+7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-2360340	$-9*(87+6*5+4^3)^2-1$	-2431431	$-9-(8+7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-2360358	$-9*(87+6*5+4^3)^2+1$	-2436609	$(98-7^6*5)*(4+3/21)$
-2360655	$-9*(87+65+4^3)^2-1$	-2436917	$98-7^6*5*(4+3/21)$
-2360663	$-9*(87+65+4^3)^2+1$	-2437113	$-98-7^6*5*(4+3/21)$
-2360665	$-9*(87+65+4^3)^2-1$	-2437421	$(98+7^6*5)*(-4-3/21)$
-2360673	$-9*(87+65+4^3)^2+1$	-2456313	$(9+8)*(7^6+5-4^3)^2+1$
-2360951	$9*(8*(7-6*5)-4^3)^2+1$	-2456347	$(9+8)*(7^6+5-4^3)^2-1$
-2360953	$9*(8*(7-6*5)-4^3)^2-1$	-2463811	$98-(7^6-5*4^3)*21$
-2361113	$9*(8-7*6*5-4^3)^2+1$	-2464007	$-98-(7^6-5*4^3)*21$
-2361115	$9*(8-7*6*5-4^3)^2-1$	-2466077	$9+(8-7^6+5^4/3)*21$
-2361257	$-9*(8+7*6*5+4^3)^2+1$	-2466095	$-9+(8-7^6+5^4/3)*21$
-2361259	$-9*(8+7*6*5+4^3)^2-1$	-2466156	$98-(7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-2361545	$-9*((8*7-6)*5+4^3)^2+1$	-2466352	$-98-(7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-2361547	$-9*((8*7-6)*5+4^3)^2-1$	-2466413	$9-(8+7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-2362085	$-9*((8*7+6)*5+4^3)^2+1$	-2466431	$-9-(8+7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-2362087	$-9*((8*7+6)*5+4^3)^2-1$	-2467692	$-9*876*((5^4+3)/2-1)$
-2362347	$9*((8-76)*5-4^3)^2+1$	-2469271	$98-(7^6-5*4^3)*21$
-2362679	$-9*(8*(7*6+5)+4^3)^2+1$	-2469467	$-98-(7^6-5*4^3)*21$
-2362681	$-9*(8*(7*6+5)+4^3)^2-1$	-2469796	$98-(7^6-5*(4+3))*21$
-2362779	$-9*(8+76*5+4^3)^2-1$	-2469964	$98-(7^6-(5+4)*3)*21$
-2362797	$-9*(8+76*5+4^3)^2+1$	-2469992	$-98-(7^6-5*(4+3))*21$
-2363454	$-9*(8+7*65+4^3)^2-1$	-2470079	$-9-8-(7^6-(5+4)*3)*21$
-2363975	$-9*(8*(7+6)*5+4^3)^2+1$	-2470134	$-9*(8+(7^6/(5+4)-3))*21$
-2363977	$-9*(8*(7+6)*5+4^3)^2-1$	-2470160	$-98-(7^6-(5+4)*3)*21$
-2366100	$9*(8-765-4^3)^2+1$	-2470179	$9*8-(7^6-54/3)*21$
-2366118	$9*(8-765-4^3)^2-1$	-2470234	$9+8-(7^6-54/3)*21$
-2366244	$-9*(8+765+4^3)^2-1$	-2470250	$9-8-(7^6-54/3)*21$
-2367126	$-9*(876-5+4^3)^2-1$	-2470252	$-9+8-(7^6-54/3)*21$
-2367216	$-9*(876+5+4^3)^2-1$	-2470268	$-9-8-(7^6-54/3)*21$
-2367234	$-9*(876+5+4^3)^2+1$	-2470384	$98-(7^6+5-4^3)*21$
-2369484	$9*(8-7^6)-5*(4^3)^2-1$	-2470454	$98-(7^6-5+4/3)*21$
-2369494	$9*(8-7^6)-5*(4^3)^2+1$	-2470516	$98-(7^6-5/(4+3))*21$
-2369628	$-9*(8+7^6)-5*(4^3)^2-1$	-2470742	$-98-(7^6+5/(4+3))*21$
-2369638	$-9*(8+7^6)-5*(4^3)^2+1$	-2470804	$-98-(7^6+5-4/3)*21$
-2369689	$98-7^6*(5*4+3/21)$	-2470867	$-98-(7^6+5*4/3)*21$
-2369885	$-98-7^6*(5*4+3/21)$	-2470874	$-98-(7^6-5+4*3)*21$
-2374415	$-9*(8*7*6*5+4^3)^2+1$	-2470990	$9+8-(7^6+54/3)*21$
-2374417	$-9*(8*7*6*5+4^3)^2-1$	-2471006	$9-8-(7^6+54/3)*21$
-2379320	$(9+8)*(7-6^4(-5+4^3)/2+1)$	-2471008	$-9+8-(7^6+54/3)*21$
-2379558	$(-9-8)*(7+6^4(-5+4^3)/2-1)$	-2471024	$-9-8-(7^6+54/3)*21$
-2379592	$(-9-8)*(7+6^4(-5+4^3)/2+1)$	-2471079	$-9*8-(7^6+54/3)*21$
-2382362	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)/4^3)^2+1$	-2471098	$98-(7^6+(5+4)*3)*21$
-2382364	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)/4^3)^2-1$	-2471266	$98-(7^6+5*(4+3))*21$
-2382383	$9-(8/(7^6*5^4*3-2))^4-1$	-2471294	$-98-(7^6+(5+4)*3)*21$
-2382401	$-9-(8/(7^6*5^4*3-2))^4-1$	-2471462	$-98-(7^6+5*(4+3))*21$
-2382777	$-9*(87*6*5+4^3)^2-1$	-2471791	$98-(7^6+5*4^3)*21$
-2382795	$-9*(87*6*5+4^3)^2+1$	-2471987	$-98-(7^6+5*4^3)*21$
-2386647	$-9*(8*76*5+4^3)^2-1$	-2474827	$9+(8-7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-2386665	$-9*(8*76*5+4^3)^2+1$	-2474845	$-9+(8-7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-2386692	$-98*((7+6)*5^4*3-21)$	-2474906	$98-(7^6+5^4/3)*21$
-2391200	$-98*((7+6)*(5^4*3+2)-1)$	-2475102	$-98-(7^6+5^4/3)*21$
-2392047	$-9*(8*7*65+4^3)^2-1$	-2475163	$9-(8+7^6+5^4/3)*21$
-2398707	$-9*(876*5+4^3)^2-1$	-2475181	$-9-(8+7^6+5^4/3)*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2477251	$98 - (7^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3)^* 21$	-2820768	$-9 \cdot 8^* ((7^6 - 54)/3 - 21)$
-2477447	$-98 - (7^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3)^* 21$	-2821512	$9^* ((-8^* 7^6 + 5^4)/3 + 21)$
-2499918	$(-9 - 8)^* ((7^6 - 5)/4)^*(3+2) - 1$	-2821890	$9^* ((-8^* 7^6 + 5^4)/3 - 21)$
-2499952	$(-9 - 8)^* ((7^6 - 5)/4)^*(3+2) + 1$	-2821938	$9 - (8^* 7^6 - 543)^*(2+1)$
-2509906	$98 - (7^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3)^* 21$	-2821956	$-9 - (8^* 7^6 - 543)^*(2+1)$
-2510102	$-98 - (7^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3)^* 21$	-2822091	$-9^* (8^* (7^6 - 54)/3 - 21)$
-2510163	$9 - (8^* 7^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3)^* 21$	-2822103	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 54)^* 3 - 21)$
-2510181	$-9 - (8^* 7^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3)^* 21$	-2822121	$-9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 54)^* 3 - 21)$
-2520228	$-9^* (87 + 6^{\wedge}(-5 + 4^* 3)) - 21$	-2822199	$9 - 8^* (7^6 - 54 - 3)^*(2+1)$
-2530575	$(9^* (8+7)^{\wedge} - 6 / (5^{\wedge} - 4/3 - 2))^{\wedge} - 1$	-2822217	$-9 - 8^* (7^6 - 54 - 3)^*(2+1)$
-2531925	$(-9^* (8+7)^{\wedge} - 6 / (5^{\wedge} - 4/3 + 2))^{\wedge} - 1$	-2822247	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 54)^* 3 - 2 - 1)$
-2534687	$(-9 / (87^* (65 + 4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2)))^{\wedge} - 1$	-2822267	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 54)^* 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-2539056	$(-9 + (8+7)/6)^*(5^4 \cdot 3/2) - 1$	-2822275	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 54)^* 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-2539069	$(-9 + (8+7)/6)^*(5^4 \cdot 3/2) + 1$	-2822293	$-9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 54)^* 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-2546183	$9 - 8^* (7^6 + 5^4 \cdot 321)$	-2822295	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 54)^* 3 + 2 + 1)$
-2546201	$-9 - 8^* (7^6 + 5^4 \cdot 321)$	-2822313	$-9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 54)^* 3 + 2 + 1)$
-2571399	$9^* (8 - 7^6 \cdot (54 - 3)/21)$	-2822343	$9 - 8^* (7^6 - 54 + 3)^*(2+1)$
-2571543	$-9^* (8 + 7^6 \cdot (54 - 3)/21)$	-2822415	$9 - 8^* (7^6 - 5 - 43)^*(2+1)$
-2621380	$(9 + (8 - 7)^{\wedge} 6)^*(5 - 4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	-2822433	$-9 - 8^* (7^6 - 5 - 43)^*(2+1)$
-2621500	$(9 + (8 - 7)^{\wedge} 6)^*(5 - 4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-2822439	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 54)^* 3 + 21)$
-2627508	$98 - (7^6 + 5)^*(4/3 + 21)$	-2822457	$-9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 54)^* 3 + 21)$
-2627704	$-98 - (7^6 + 5)^*(4/3 + 21)$	-2822469	$-9^* (8^* (7^6 - 54)/3 + 21)$
-2638531	$98 - (7^6 + (5^4)^{\wedge} 3)^* 21$	-2822655	$9 - 8^* (7^6 + 5 - 43)^*(2+1)$
-2638727	$-98 - (7^6 + (5^4)^{\wedge} 3)^* 21$	-2822922	$9 - (8^* 7^6 - 5^4 \cdot 3)^*(2+1)$
-2646998	$9^* (8 - (7^6 \cdot 5 - 4 - 3)/2) + 1$	-2822998	$98 - (7^6 - 5^4)^*(3+21)$
-2647000	$9^* (8 - (7^6 \cdot 5 - 4 - 3)/2) - 1$	-2823135	$9 - 8^* (7^6 - 54/3)^*(2+1)$
-2647027	$9^* (8 - (7^6 \cdot 5 - 4 + 3)/2) - 1$	-2823183	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 5 - 4)^* 3 - 21)$
-2647178	$-9^* (8 + (7^6 \cdot 5 + 4 - 3)/2) + 1$	-2823194	$-98 - (7^6 - 5^4)^*(3+21)$
-2647205	$-9^* (8 + (7^6 \cdot 5 + 4 + 3)/2) + 1$	-2823262	$98 - (7^6 - 5 - 4)^*(3+21)$
-2647207	$-9^* (8 + (7^6 \cdot 5 + 4 + 3)/2) - 1$	-2823383	$9^* 8 - (7^6 - 5)^* 4^* 3^* 2 + 1$
-2647359	$-9^* (8 + (7^6 \cdot 5 + 43)/2 - 1)$	-2823502	$98 - (7^6 + 5 - 4)^*(3+21)$
-2658595	$(9 + 8/7)^*(6^* 5 - 4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-2823650	$-98 - (7^6 - 5 + 4)^*(3+21)$
-2660161	$(-9^* (8^* (7 + 6 - 5^4) + 3)^{\wedge} - 2)^{\wedge} - 1$	-2823769	$9^* 8 - (7^6 + 5)^* 4^* 3^* 2 - 1$
-2666773	$(-9 - 8)^* ((7^6 + 5)^* 4/3 - 2 - 1)$	-2823867	$-9^* (8^* (7^6 + 5^4)/3 - 21)$
-2666875	$(-9 - 8)^* ((7^6 + 5)^* 4/3 + 2 + 1)$	-2823890	$-98 - (7^6 + 5 + 4)^*(3+21)$
-2677483	$(-9 - 8)^*(7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3^* 2 - 1)$	-2823951	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 + 5 + 4)^* 3 + 21)$
-2677491	$9 + (8 - 76)^* 5^4 \cdot 3^* 21$	-2823958	$98 - (7^6 + 5^4)^*(3+21)$
-2677517	$(-9 - 8)^*(7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3^* 2 + 1)$	-2823999	$9 - 8^* (7^6 + 54/3)^*(2+1)$
-2699181	$9^* ((8+7)^*(6 - 5^4 \cdot 32) + 1)$	-2824017	$-9 - 8^* (7^6 + 54/3)^*(2+1)$
-2700801	$-9^* ((8+7)^*(6 + 5^4 \cdot 32) - 1)$	-2824154	$-98 - (7^6 + 5^4)^*(3+21)$
-2705714	$98 - (7^6 - 5)^*(4^* 3^* 2 - 1)$	-2824479	$9 - 8^* (7^6 - 5 + 43)^*(2+1)$
-2705808	$98 - 7^6 \cdot (5^4 + 3) + 21$	-2824683	$-9^* (8^* (7^6 + 54)/3 - 21)$
-2705850	$98 - 7^6 \cdot (5^4 + 3) - 21$	-2824695	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 + 54)^* 3 - 21)$
-2705884	$9^* - 8 - (7^6 - 5)^*(4^* 3^* 2 - 1)$	-2824713	$-9 - 8^* ((7^6 + 54)^* 3 - 21)$
-2708811	$(-9 - 8 / (7 - 6 + 5))^*(4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-2824791	$9 - 8^* (7^6 + 54 - 3)^*(2+1)$
-2710176	$(-9 - 87/65)^*(4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	-2824839	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 + 54)^* 3 - 2 - 1)$
-2734228	$98 + 7^*(6 - 5^4 \cdot 3/2) + 1$	-2824859	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 + 54)^* 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-2734242	$98 + 7^*(6 - 5^4 \cdot 3/2) - 1$	-2824867	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 + 54)^* 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-2734508	$-98 - 7^*(6 + 5^4 \cdot 3/2) - 1$	-2824887	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 + 54)^* 3 + 2 + 1)$
-2745176	$-98^*(7^6 \cdot 5^4 + 3)/21$	-2824935	$9 - 8^* (7^6 + 54 + 3)^*(2+1)$
-2745442	$-98^*(7^6 \cdot 5^4 + 3)/21$	-2825031	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 + 54)^* 3 + 21)$
-2778111	$-9/8^*(7^6 - 54 - 3)^* 21$	-2825049	$-9 - 8^* ((7^6 + 54)^* 3 + 21)$
-2778549	$(9 - 8^*(7^6 - 5^4 \cdot 3))^*(2+1)$	-2825061	$-9^*(8^*(7^6 + 54)/3 + 21)$
-2778603	$(9 + 8^*(7^6 - 5^4 \cdot 3))^*(-2 - 1)$	-2825196	$9 - (8^* 7^6 + 543)^*(2+1)$
-2784537	$-9/8^*(7^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3)^* 21$	-2825214	$-9 - (8^* 7^6 + 543)^*(2+1)$
-2791353	$9^* (-8^{\wedge} 7/6 + 5^4 \cdot 3^* 21)$	-2825262	$-9^* ((8^* 7^6 + 5^4)/3 - 21)$
-2799860	$(-98 - 7^6)^*(5^4 \cdot 32 - 1)$	-2825640	$-9^* ((8^* 7^6 + 5^4)/3 + 21)$
-2800140	$(-98 - 7^6)^*(5^4 \cdot 32 + 1)$	-2826384	$-9^* 8^* ((7^6 + 54)/3 + 21)$
-2808387	$-9^*(8^*(7^6 - 5^4)/3 - 21)$	-2827455	$9 - 8^* (7^6 + 54 \cdot 3)^*(2+1)$
-2808399	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 5^4)^* 3 - 21)$	-2827791	$9^{\wedge} (8 + 7 - 6 - 5)^*(-432 + 1)$
-2808417	$-9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 5^4)^* 3 - 21)$	-2828549	$(9 - 8^*(7^6 + 5^4/3))^*(2+1)$
-2808478	$98 - (7^6 - 5^4)^*(3 + 21)$	-2828603	$(-9 - 8^*(7^6 + 5^4/3))^*(2+1)$
-2808674	$-98 - (7^6 - 5^4)^*(3 + 21)$	-2828727	$9 - 8^* (7^6 + 5^4 \cdot 3)^*(2+1)$
-2808735	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 5^4)^* 3 + 21)$	-2831949	$-9^*(87 + 6/5^*(4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 + 1))$
-2808753	$-9 - 8^* ((7^6 - 5^4)^* 3 + 21)$	-2836599	$9 - 8^* (7^6 + 543)^*(2+1)$
-2808765	$-9^*(8^*(7^6 - 5^4)/3 + 21)$	-2836617	$-9 - 8^* (7^6 + 543)^*(2+1)$
-2810535	$9 - 8^*(7^6 - 543)^*(2+1)$	-2838387	$-9^*(8^*(7^6 + 5^4)/3 - 21)$
-2810553	$-9 - 8^*(7^6 - 543)^*(2+1)$	-2838399	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 + 5^4)^* 3 - 21)$
-2818407	$9 - 8^*(7^6 - 5^4 \cdot 3)^*(2+1)$	-2838417	$-9 - 8^* ((7^6 + 5^4)^* 3 - 21)$
-2818549	$(9 - 8^*(7^6 - 5^4 \cdot 3))^*(2+1)$	-2838478	$98 - (7^6 + 5^4)^*(3+21)$
-2818603	$(-9 - 8^*(7^6 - 5^4 \cdot 3))^*(2+1)$	-2838674	$-98 - (7^6 + 5^4)^*(3+21)$
-2819679	$9 - 8^*(7^6 - 54 \cdot 3)^*(2+1)$	-2838735	$9 - 8^* ((7^6 + 5^4)^* 3 + 21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2838753	$-9 \cdot 8^*((7^6+5^4)^3+21)$	-2885658	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4+32)+1$
-2838765	$-9^*(8^*(7^6+5^4)/3+21)$	-2885659	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4+32)^{\wedge}1$
-2840913	$9^{\wedge}(8+7-6-5)^*(-432-1)$	-2885660	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4+32)-1$
-2857173	$(-9-8)^*(7^6*5/(4+3)^2-1)$	-2885757	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4+32+1)$
-2857207	$(-9-8)^*(7^6*5/(4+3)^2+1)$	-2888452	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+3^*21)$
-2864394	$9^*(8-7^6-5^4*321)$	-2888697	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4+3^*21)$
-2864538	$-9^*(8+7^6+5^4*321)$	-2914814	$98^*7^*(6-5^4/3)^*21$
-2868549	$(9-8^*(7^6+5^4*3))^*(2+1)$	-2918663	$9^*(8^*(7-6^{\wedge}5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-2868603	$(-9-8^*(7^6+5^4*3))^*(2+1)$	-2918665	$9^*(8^*(7-6^{\wedge}5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-2869759	$((9^8+7^6)/-5+4)/3+21$	-2919671	$-9^*(8^*(7+6^{\wedge}5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-2869801	$((9^8+7^6)/-5+4)/3-21$	-2919673	$-9^*(8^*(7+6^{\wedge}5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-2873924	$9^*(8-7^6*5/(4+3)+2)+1$	-2934836	$9^*(8-7^6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-2873926	$9^*(8-7^6*5/(4+3)+2)-1$	-2934838	$9^*(8-7^6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-2874068	$-9^*(8+7^6*5/(4+3)+2)+1$	-2934980	$-9^*(8+7^6*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-2874070	$-9^*(8+7^6*5/(4+3)+2)-1$	-2934982	$-9^*(8+7^6*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-2876349	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4-3^*21)$	-2939223	$98-7^*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2877605	$((9^8+7^6)/-5-4)/3+21$	-2939249	$9^*8-7^*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2877647	$((9^8+7^6)/-5-4)/3-21$	-2939263	$9^*8-7^*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2879044	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4-32-1)$	-2939393	$-9^*8-7^*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2879141	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4-32)+1$	-2939407	$-9^*8-7^*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2879142	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4-32)^{\wedge}1$	-2939433	$-98-7^*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2879143	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4-32)-1$	-2941002	$98-(7^6-5)^*(4^*3^*2+1)$
-2879240	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4-32+1)$	-2941198	$-98-(7^6-5)^*(4^*3^*2+1)$
-2879289	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4-32-1)$	-2941252	$98-(7^6+5)^*(4^*3^*2+1)$
-2879386	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4-32)+1$	-2941422	$9^*-8-(7^6+5)^*(4^*3^*2+1)$
-2879387	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4-32)^{\wedge}1$	-2945103	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7/6+5^{\wedge}4^*321$
-2879388	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4-32)-1$	-2959852	$(-9^*8-76)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32-1)$
-2879485	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4-32+1)$	-2960103	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7/6+5^{\wedge}4^*(32+1))$
-2879632	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-2960148	$(-9^*8-76)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$
-2879877	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-2965719	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4^*32-1)$
-2879926	$98^*((7^6-5)/-4+3+21)$	-2965737	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$
-2880171	$98^*((7^6+5)/-4+3+21)$	-2971353	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7/6+5^{\wedge}4^*(32-1))$
-2880514	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+3-21)$	-2974767	$9^*(8+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)/21)$
-2880759	$98^*((7^6+5)/-4-3+21)$	-2974911	$9^*(-8+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)/21)$
-2881298	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2984095	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5^{\wedge}4)^3/2-1)$
-2881494	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4-3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-2984129	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5^{\wedge}4)^3/2+1)$
-2881543	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2999803	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5-4)^3/2-1)$
-2881592	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4-3^*2-1)$	-2999905	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5)/4^*3^*2-1)$
-2881739	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4-3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-3000007	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5+4)^3/2-1)$
-2881837	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4-3^*2-1)$	-3000092	$(-9-8)^*((7^6+5-4)^3/2+1)$
-2881963	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4-3)+21$	-3000194	$(-9-8)^*((7^6+5)/4^*3^*2+1)$
-2882005	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4-3)-21$	-3000262	$(-9-8)^*((7^6+5+4)^3/2-1)$
-2882208	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4-3)+21$	-3000296	$(-9-8)^*((7^6+5+4)^3/2+1)$
-2882250	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4-3)-21$	-3014702	$(9+(8+7)/6)^*(-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2882264	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4-3/21)$	-3014725	$(9+(8+7)/6)^*(-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2882292	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+3/21)$	-3015970	$(-9-8)^*((7^6+5^{\wedge}4)^3/2-1)$
-2882509	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4-3/21)$	-3016004	$(-9-8)^*((7^6+5^{\wedge}4)^3/2+1)$
-2882537	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4+3/21)$	-3027036	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7/6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$
-2882551	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+3)+21$	-3028170	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7/6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
-2882593	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+3)-21$	-3044478	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6+5^{\wedge}4*(3-21))$
-2882796	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4+3)+21$	-3070782	$(9-87)^*(-6+5^{\wedge}4^*3^*21)$
-2882838	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4+3)-21$	-3071718	$(9-87)^*(6+5^{\wedge}4^*3^*21)$
-2882964	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+3^*2+1)$	-3087686	$98^*7^*(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*-21$
-2883062	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-3092479	$9-8^*7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)/21$
-2883209	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4+3^*2+1)$	-3124375	$9+8^*(76-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-2883258	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-3124391	$9+8^*(76-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-2883307	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-3124393	$-9+8^*(76-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-2883503	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-3124409	$-9+8^*(76-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-2883708	$-9^*(8+7)-(6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-3125591	$9-8^*(76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-2883730	$-9^*(8+7)-(6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-3125607	$9-8^*(76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-2884042	$98^*((7^6-5)/-4+3-21)$	-3125609	$-9-8^*(76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-2884287	$98^*((7^6+5)/-4+3-21)$	-3126030	$9^*(8-7^6*(5-43/21))$
-2884630	$98^*((7^6-5)/-4-3-21)$	-3126174	$-9^*(8+7^6*(5-43/21))$
-2884875	$98^*((7^6+5)/-4-3-21)$	-3128664	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4^*3-21)$
-2884924	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-3144042	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7/6+5^{\wedge}4/3-21)$
-2885169	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-3157839	$-9^*87/65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2885316	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+32-1)$	-3159387	$9^*(8-(7^6-5^{\wedge}4)^3+21)$
-2885413	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+32)+1$	-3159531	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5^{\wedge}4)^3-21)$
-2885414	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+32)^{\wedge}1$	-3159765	$9^*(8-(7^6-5^{\wedge}4)^3-21)$
-2885415	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+32)-1$	-3159909	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5^{\wedge}4)^3+21)$
-2885512	$-98^*((7^6-5)/4+32+1)$	-3161790	$9^*(8-(7^6-5^{\wedge}43)^*(2+1))$
-2885561	$-98^*((7^6+5)/4+32-1)$	-3162792	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4^*3-21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-3170646	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5*43)^*(2+1))$	-3294411	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-32)-1$
-3170790	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5*43)^*(2+1))$	-3294471	$9-(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4/3)^*21$
-3172077	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54*3)^*(2+1))$	-3294739	$-9^*(8*7^{\wedge}6/54+3)^*21$
-3172221	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54*3)^*(2+1))$	-3295675	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-3174804	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3+21)$	-3296090	$(98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4/3)^*-21$
-3174912	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54-3)^*(2+1))$	-3296370	$(98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4/3)^*-21$
-3174972	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3)+21$	-3298708	$-9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6/54+3)^*21$
-3175014	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3)-21$	-3307491	$9-(8+76)^*5^{\wedge}4*3^*21$
-3175056	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54-3)^*(2+1))$	-3307509	$-9-(8+76)^*5^{\wedge}4*3^*21$
-3175116	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3)+21$	-3307598	$-98^*(7+6^*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-3175158	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3)-21$	-3317865	$(-9-876)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3^*2-1)$
-3175164	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3+2+1)$	-3319635	$(-9-876)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3^*2+1)$
-3175182	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3-21)$	-3320103	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
-3175218	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54+3)^*(2+1))$	-3325719	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4*3^*2+1)$
-3175326	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3+21)$	-3325737	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4*3^*2-1)$
-3175569	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5-43)^*(2+1))$	-3325751	$9^*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-3175965	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54/3)^*(2+1))$	-3325753	$9^*(8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-3176109	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54/3)^*(2+1))$	-3331353	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$
-3176416	$98-(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)^*(2+1)$	-3333360	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)/3-2-1)$
-3176482	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))/3+2)-1$	-3333462	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)/3+2+1)$
-3176564	$-9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))/3+2)+1$	-3346353	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4*3^*21$
-3176630	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)^*(2+1)$	-3359816	$9^*8-(7^*6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-3176937	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)^*(2+1))$	-3359818	$9^*8-(7^*6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-3177027	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3+21)$	-3407696	$98+(7+6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-3177081	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)^*(2+1))$	-3407722	$9^*8+(7+6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-3177161	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-3407748	$9^*8+(7+6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-3177621	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+43)^*(2+1))$	-3407996	$-9^*8-(7+6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-3177864	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3-21)$	-3414474	$(9+87^*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^*21$
-3177888	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3)+21$	-3414852	$(-9+87^*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^*21$
-3178026	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3-2-1)$	-3436776	$(-9-87^*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^*21$
-3178032	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3)+21$	-3450512	$(-9+(8-7)/6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-3178062	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3+2-1)$	-3466788	$(-9+8^{\wedge}(8-7+6))^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-3178074	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3)-21$	-3472244	$-9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-3178080	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3+2+1)$	-3472254	$-9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-3178134	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54+3)^*(2+1))$	-3478977	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)/21)$
-3178242	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3+21)$	-3479121	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)/21)$
-3180825	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+54*3)^*(2+1))$	-3484656	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))/-21$
-3180969	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54*3)^*(2+1))$	-3500103	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6+5^{\wedge}4*3^*21)$
-3182256	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5*43)^*(2+1))$	-3507732	$9^*(876-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3182400	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5*43)^*(2+1))$	-3507750	$9^*(876-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-3191112	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+543)^*(2+1))$	-3510144	$9^*(8^*76-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3191256	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+543)^*(2+1))$	-3510162	$9^*(8^*76-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-3193137	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3+21)$	-3510918	$9^*(87^*6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3193281	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3-21)$	-3514779	$9^*(87+6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3193515	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3-21)$	-3514797	$9^*(87+6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-3193659	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3+21)$	-3514860	$9^*(8+76-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3202689	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)/(3-21)$	-3514878	$9^*(8+76-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-3246978	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7/6+5^{\wedge}4*(3-21))$	-3514887	$9^*(87-6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3250383	$(9-876)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3^*2-1)$	-3515004	$-9^*(8-76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-3252117	$(9-876)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3^*2+1)$	-3515022	$-9^*(8-76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3255168	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6)^*(5^*4/3+21)$	-3516228	$9^*(8-76-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3257667	$(98+7^{\wedge}6)^*(-5^*4/3-21)$	-3516363	$-9^*(87-6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3263286	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$	-3516372	$-9^*(8+76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-3264420	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$	-3516390	$-9^*(8+76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3275232	$(-9+8/(7+6))^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	-3516453	$-9^*(87+6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-3277116	$-9^*876*(5^{\wedge}4/3^*2-1)$	-3516471	$-9^*(87+6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3289636	$-9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6/54-3)^*21$	-3518270	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))/-21$
-3291974	$(98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4/3)^*21$	-3520314	$-9^*(87^*6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-3292254	$(98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4/3)^*21$	-3520332	$-9^*(87^*6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3292651	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-3521088	$-9^*(8^*76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-3292669	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-3521106	$-9^*(8^*76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3292884	$-9^*876*(5^{\wedge}4/3^*2+1)$	-3523518	$-9^*(876+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-3293605	$-9^*(8*7^{\wedge}6/54-3)^*21$	-3523859	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2)+1$
-3293855	$9+(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4/3)^*21$	-3523861	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2)-1$
-3293873	$-9+(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4/3)^*21$	-3524003	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2)+1$
-3293933	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-32)+1$	-3524005	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2)-1$
-3293935	$98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-32)-1$	-3524283	$-9^*87^*(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$
-3293974	$9-(8*7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-3526767	$-9^*((8^*7^{\wedge}6-54^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
-3294129	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-32)+1$	-3527118	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*5/4)^*(3+21)$
-3294352	$9-(8*7^{\wedge}6+54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-3529269	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5/4)^*(3+21)$
-3294370	$-9-(8*7^{\wedge}6+54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-3529287	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5/4)^*(3+21)$
-3294409	$-98+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-32)+1$	-3529375	$9^*8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)^*3^*2-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-3529565	$9^* - 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4) * 3 * 2 + 1$	-3765167	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 + 32 - 1)$
-3529653	$9 - (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / 4) * (3 + 21)$	-3765183	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 + 32 + 1)$
-3531087	$(9 + 8) * (7 * 6^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-3765240	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 - 321$
-3531121	$(9 + 8) * (7 * 6^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-3765258	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 - 321$
-3531822	$(98 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / 4) * (-3 - 21)$	-3765423	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 + 3 * 21)$
-3564444	$(-9 - 8^{\wedge}(-7 + 6)) * (5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) - 1)$	-3766487	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * (3 + 2 - 1)$
-3565163	$9 + (8 - 76) / 5 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-3767167	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4 + 321)$
-3580720	$(-9 - (8 - 7) / 6) * (5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) - 1)$	-3767185	$-9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4 + 321)$
-3582579	$(98 - 7) * (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 * 21)$	-3778344	$9 * (87 - (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 / 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-3583671	$(-98 + 7) * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 * 21)$	-3778362	$9 * (87 - (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 / 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-3627646	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 - 1)$	-3778631	$9 * (8 * 7 - (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 / 3)^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-3627842	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 - 1)$	-3778633	$9 * (8 * 7 - (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 / 3)^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-3645428	$9 + 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (32 - 1)$	-3779000	$9 * (8 + 7 - (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 / 3)^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-3645444	$9 - 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (32 - 1)$	-3779002	$9 * (8 + 7 - (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 / 3)^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-3645446	$-9 + 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (32 - 1)$	-3779270	$-9 * (8 + 7 + (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 / 3)^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-3645462	$-9 - 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (32 - 1)$	-3779272	$-9 * (8 + 7 + (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 / 3)^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-3646401	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4) * (32 - 1)$	-3779639	$-9 * (8 * 7 + (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 / 3)^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-3646597	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4) * (32 - 1)$	-3779641	$-9 * (8 * 7 + (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 / 3)^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-3646742	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * (32 - 1)$	-3779910	$-9 * (87 + (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 / 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-3646866	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 - 1)$	-3780576	$(-9 - 87) * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 * 21)$
-3646892	$9 * 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 - 1)$	-3783026	$-9 / ((8 - 7 + 6^{\wedge}5 / 4) / 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-3646938	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * (32 - 1)$	-3800992	$9 + 87 / 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-3646990	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * (32 - 1)$	-3801021	$9 + 87 / 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-3647036	$-9 * 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 - 1)$	-3801137	$9 - 87 / 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-3647062	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 - 1)$	-3801166	$9 - 87 / 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-3647176	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 - 1)$	-3804858	$9 * 87 * ((6 + 5)^{\wedge}4 / -3 + 21)$
-3647186	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * (32 - 1)$	-3820726	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) / 3 - 21)$
-3647202	$9 * 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 - 1)$	-3822490	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) / 3 - 2 - 1)$
-3647248	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * (32 - 1)$	-3822735	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) / 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-3647300	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * (32 - 1)$	-3822833	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) / 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-3647346	$-9 * 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 - 1)$	-3823078	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) / 3 + 2 + 1)$
-3647372	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 - 1)$	-3824842	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) / 3 + 21)$
-3647496	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * (32 - 1)$	-3841110	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) / 3 - 21)$
-3647641	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) * (32 - 1)$	-3841796	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) / 3 - 21)$
-3647837	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) * (32 - 1)$	-3843119	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) / 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-3648776	$9 + 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * (32 - 1)$	-3843217	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) / 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-3648792	$9 - 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * (32 - 1)$	-3843560	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) / 3 - 2 - 1)$
-3648794	$-9 + 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * (32 - 1)$	-3843805	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) / 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-3648810	$-9 - 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * (32 - 1)$	-3843903	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) / 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-3661686	$(9 - (87 + 6) * 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * 21$	-3844148	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) / 3 + 2 + 1)$
-3661866	$9 - (87 + 6) * 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 * 21$	-3845226	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) / 3 + 21)$
-3661884	$-9 - (87 + 6) * 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 * 21$	-3845912	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) / 3 + 21)$
-3662064	$(9 + (87 + 6) * 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * -21$	-3856349	$98 * (7 / 6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * 21$
-3666396	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 - 1)$	-3857476	$98 * (7 + 6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 * 21)$
-3666592	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 - 1)$	-3860024	$-98 * (7 + 6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3 * 21)$
-3669092	$98 / 7 * (65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-3861151	$-98 * (7 / 6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * 21$
-3669105	$98 / 7 * (65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$	-3861694	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 + 1)$
-3669107	$98 / 7 * (65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$	-3861890	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 + 1)$
-3670912	$-98 / 7 * (65 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-3880618	$9 + 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (32 + 1)$
-3670925	$-98 / 7 * (65 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$	-3880634	$9 - 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (32 + 1)$
-3670927	$-98 / 7 * (65 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$	-3880636	$-9 + 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (32 + 1)$
-3670940	$-98 / 7 * (65 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-3880652	$-9 - 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (32 + 1)$
-3674314	$98 * (7 - 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1))$	-3881659	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4) * (32 + 1)$
-3674816	$9 * 8 - (7 * 6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-3882022	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * (32 + 1)$
-3674818	$9 * 8 - (7 * 6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-3882218	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * (32 + 1)$
-3675686	$-98 * (7 + 6 * 5^{\wedge}4 * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1))$	-3882286	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * (32 + 1)$
-3728049	$(9 + 8) * ((-7^{\wedge}6 + (5 * 4)^{\wedge}3) * 2 + 1)$	-3882300	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4 / 3) - 21)$
-3728083	$(9 + 8) * ((-7^{\wedge}6 + (5 * 4)^{\wedge}3) * 2 - 1)$	-3882326	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4 / 3) + 2) + 1$
-3756000	$(-9 - 8 / (7 + 6)) * (5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2) - 1)$	-3882328	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4 / 3) + 2) - 1$
-3762031	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4 - 321)$	-3882352	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * (32 + 1)$
-3762049	$-9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4 - 321)$	-3882362	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4 / 3) - 2) + 1$
-3762351	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 - 321)$	-3882364	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4 / 3) - 2) - 1$
-3762369	$-9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 - 321)$	-3882470	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4 / 3) - 2) + 1$
-3763031	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) * (3 + 2 - 1)$	-3882472	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4 / 3) - 2) - 1$
-3764278	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4 + 321$	-3882482	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * (32 + 1)$
-3764296	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4 + 321$	-3882506	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4 / 3) + 2) + 1$
-3764335	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4 - 32 - 1)$	-3882508	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 4 / 3) + 2) - 1$
-3764351	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4 - 32 + 1)$	-3882548	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * (32 + 1)$
-3764415	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 - 3 * 21)$	-3882616	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * (32 + 1)$
-3765063	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 - 3 + 21)$	-3882812	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * (32 + 1)$
-3765103	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4 + 3 * 21)$	-3883175	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) * (32 + 1)$
-3765111	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 + 3 + 21)$	-3884182	$9 + 8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) * (32 + 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-3884198	$9-8-(7^6+54)*(32+1)$	-4069913	$-9-8*(7^6*5-43^{(2+1)})$
-3884200	$-9+8-(7^6+54)*(32+1)$	-4115629	$(98-(7^6*5-4)/3)^*21$
-3884216	$-9-8-(7^6+54)*(32+1)$	-4115685	$(98-(7^6*5+4)/3)^*21$
-3887757	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*((5^4)^{\wedge}3^*-2+1)$	-4117510	$9+(8-(7^6*5-4)/3)^*21$
-3888243	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*((5^4)^{\wedge}3^*-2-1)$	-4117528	$-9+(8-(7^6*5-4)/3)^*21$
-3902944	$98-(7^6+5^4)^*(32+1)$	-4117566	$9+(8-(7^6*5+4)/3)^*21$
-3903140	$-98-(7^6+5^4)^*(32+1)$	-4117584	$-9+(8-(7^6*5+4)/3)^*21$
-3929271	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)/4-321)$	-4117589	$98-(7^6*5-4)/3^*21$
-3931161	$9+(8+7)*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-4117846	$9-(8+(7^6*5-4)/3)^*21$
-3933111	$9-(8+7)*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-4117902	$9-(8+(7^6*5+4)/3)^*21$
-3933141	$9-(8+7)*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-4119745	$(98+(7^6*5-4)/3)^*-21$
-3935049	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)/4+321)$	-4119801	$(98+(7^6*5+4)/3)^*-21$
-3936299	$(9+8)*((-7^6+5^4*3)^*2+1)$	-4133745	$(98+7)*(6-5^4*3^*21)$
-3936333	$(9+8)*((-7^6+5^4*3)^*2-1)$	-4135005	$(-98-7)*(6+5^4*3^*21)$
-3978697	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^4-3)^*2-1)$	-4156950	$(-9-8/7^6)*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-3978731	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^4-3)^*2+1)$	-4159674	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*(5^4/3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-3978901	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^4+3)^*2-1)$	-4183096	$(-9+8*(7^6*5+4))^*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-3978935	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^4+3)^*2+1)$	-4193992	$-9-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)/4+321$
-3980097	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$	-4194616	$9-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)/4-321$
-3981587	$(-9-8)*((7^6-543)^*2-1)$	-4215807	$-9*(8*(7^6-543)/2-1)$
-3981621	$(-9-8)*((7^6-543)^*2+1)$	-4215888	$-9*8*((7^6-543)/2+1)$
-3989169	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5*4^{\wedge}3)^*2-1)$	-4232223	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*4+321)$
-3989203	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5*4^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$	-4233303	$-9*(8*(7^6-54-3)/2-1)$
-3997703	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2-1)$	-4233321	$-9*(8*(7^6-54-3)/2+1)$
-3997737	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$	-4233348	$9*(8-(7^6-54)^*(3+2-1))$
-3998009	$(9+8)*((-7^6+5*4*3)^*2+1)$	-4233492	$-9*(8+(7^6-54)^*(3+2-1))$
-3998043	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2-1)$	-4233519	$-9*(8*(7^6-54+3)/2-1)$
-3998077	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$	-4233627	$-9*(8*(7^6-5-43)/2-1)$
-3998859	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5*(4+3))^*2-1)$	-4233645	$-9*(8*(7^6-5-43)/2+1)$
-3998893	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5*(4+3))^*2+1)$	-4234626	$-9*((8*7^6-54*3)/2-1)$
-3999131	$(9+8)*((-7^6+(5+4)^*3)^*2+1)$	-4234707	$-9*(8*(7^6-54/3)/2-1)$
-3999165	$(9+8)*((-7^6+(5+4)^*3)^*2-1)$	-4234791	$9*(8-(7^6-5)^4+321)$
-3999267	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5*4-3)^*2-1)$	-4235273	$9*(8-7^6*(5-4+3)+2)+1$
-3999301	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5*4-3)^*2+1)$	-4235275	$9*(8-7^6*(5-4+3)+2)-1$
-3999471	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5-4*3)^*2-1)$	-4235453	$-9*(8+7^6*(5-4+3)+2)+1$
-3999505	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5-4*3)^*2+1)$	-4235455	$-9*(8+7^6*(5-4+3)+2)-1$
-3999641	$(9+8)*((7^6-5-4-3)^*-2+1)$	-4235937	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)^4)-321$
-3999675	$(9+8)*((7^6-5-4-3)^*-2-1)$	-4236021	$-9*(8*(7^6+54/3)/2+1)$
-3999845	$(9+8)*((7^6-5-4+3)^*-2+1)$	-4236723	$-9*(8*(7^6-5+43)/2-1)$
-3999889	$9-8*(7^6*(5/4+3)-21)$	-4237236	$9*(8-(7^6+54)^*(3+2-1))$
-3999907	$-9-8*(7^6*(5/4+3)-21)$	-4237380	$-9*(8+(7^6+54)^*(3+2-1))$
-4000225	$9-8*(7^6*(5/4+3)+21)$	-4238001	$9*(8-(7^6-5)^4-321)$
-4000287	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5+4-3)^*2+1)$	-4238505	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)^4+321)$
-4000457	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5+4+3)^*2-1)$	-4241187	$-9*(8*(7^6+54*3)/2-1)$
-4000491	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5+4+3)^*2+1)$	-4243095	$-9*(8*(7^6+5^4*3)/2-1)$
-4000627	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5+4*3)^*2-1)$	-4245557	$9*(8-7^6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-4000661	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5+4*3)^*2+1)$	-4245701	$-9*(8+7^6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-4000831	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^4+3)^*2-1)$	-4250442	$(-9-8)*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21)$
-4000865	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^4+3)^*2+1)$	-4250778	$(-9-8)*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21)$
-4000967	$(-9-8)*((7^6+(5+4)^*3)^*2-1)$	-4250820	$(-9-8)*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21)$
-4001001	$(-9-8)*((7^6+(5+4)^*3)^*2+1)$	-4251156	$(-9-8)*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21)$
-4001239	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5*(4+3))^*2-1)$	-4254840	$-9*8*((7^6+543)/2-1)$
-4001273	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5*(4+3))^*2+1)$	-4254903	$-9*(8*(7^6+543)/2-1)$
-4002055	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5+4^{\wedge}3)^*2-1)$	-4254921	$-9*(8*(7^6+543)/2+1)$
-4002089	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5+4^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$	-4254984	$-9*8*((7^6+543)/2+1)$
-4002395	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^*2-1)$	-4272049	$(-9-8)*((7^6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3)^*2-1)$
-4002429	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$	-4272083	$(-9-8)*((7^6+(5*4)^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$
-4010929	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^4*3)^*2-1)$	-4281081	$98*(7-(6/(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-4010963	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^4*3)^*2+1)$	-4282453	$-98*(7+(6/(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-4012008	$-9*(876-5^4/3)^{\wedge}2+1$	-4313738	$(9/((8-7^6*5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-4012010	$-9*(876-5^4/3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-4335000	$(9-876)*5^4*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-4016233	$(-9-8)*(7*6*5^4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-4404027	$9-(8+76)/5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-4016267	$(-9-8)*(7*6*5^4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-4425000	$(-9-876)*5^4*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-4018511	$(-9-8)*((7^6+543)^*2-1)$	-4443426	$(9+8)*765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$
-4018545	$(-9-8)*((7^6+543)^*2+1)$	-4443460	$(9+8)*765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-4021197	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4-3)^*-2+1)$	-4452861	$(9+8)*(7*6*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-4021231	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4-3)^*-2-1)$	-4453100	$9+(87/(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$
-4021401	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4+3)^*-2+1)$	-4453118	$-9+(87/(6-(5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2))^{\wedge}-1$
-4021435	$(9+8)*((7^6+5^4+3)^*-2-1)$	-4455122	$(9+8)*(7*(6+5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-4063799	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^4*3)^*2-1)$	-4455156	$(9+8)*(7*(6+5)-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-4063833	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^4*3)^*2+1)$	-4455326	$(9+8)*((7+6)^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-4069895	$9-8*(7^6*5-43^{(2+1)})$	-4455632	$(9+8)*(7*6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-4455666	$(9+8)*(7*6+5-4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-4709417	$-9-8*(7^6*5+432-1)$
-4456482	$(-9-8)*((7-6)^5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-4709433	$-9-8*(7^6*5+432+1)$
-4457230	$(-9-8)*(7*6+5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-4713175	$9-8*(7^6*5+43*21)$
-4460001	$(9+8)*(7*6*5-4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-4713193	$-9-8*(7^6*5+43*21)$
-4460035	$(9+8)*(7*6*5-4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-4716223	$9-8*(7^6*5+4*321)$
-4469436	$(-9-8)*(765+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-4716241	$-9-8*(7^6*5+4*321)$
-4469470	$(-9-8)*(765+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-4716703	$9-8*(7^6*5+4^3*21)$
-4492176	$(-9-(8+7)/6)*(5^4\wedge (3/2)-1)$	-4716721	$-9-8*(7^6*5+4^3*21)$
-4492199	$(-9-(8+7)/6)*(5^4\wedge (3/2)+1)$	-4717809	$-9*((8^8(7-6+5)-43)^2-1)$
-4499866	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)/4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-4717827	$-9*((8^8(7-6+5)-43)^2+1)$
-4499900	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)/4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-4718476	$98-(7+6+5)*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-4500981	$-9*((8+(7/(6/54)))^3)^2-1)$	-4719357	$-9*((8^8(7-6+5)+43)^2-1)$
-4528383	$-9*(8*7*(6+5*4/3))^2+1$	-4719375	$-9*((8^8(7-6+5)+43)^2+1)$
-4528385	$-9*(8*7*(6+5*4/3))^2-1$	-4720735	$9-8*(7^6*5+43^2-1)$
-4640575	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4\wedge (3/2)+1)$	-4720751	$9-8*(7^6*5+43^2+1)$
-4640609	$(9+8)*(7^6-5^4\wedge (3/2)-1)$	-4720753	$-9-8*(7^6*5+43^2-1)$
-4691151	$9-8*(7^6*5-43^2-1)$	-4720769	$-9-8*(7^6*5+43^2+1)$
-4691167	$9-8*(7^6*5-43^2+1)$	-4764698	$9*(8-(7^6*(5+4)-3)/2)+1$
-4691169	$-9-8*(7^6*5-43^2-1)$	-4764700	$9*(8-(7^6*(5+4)-3)/2)-1$
-4691185	$-9-8*(7^6*5-43^2+1)$	-4764725	$9*(8-(7^6*(5+4)+3)/2)+1$
-4695199	$9-8*(7^6*5-4^3*21)$	-4764727	$9*(8-(7^6*(5+4)+3)/2)-1$
-4695217	$-9-8*(7^6*5-4^3*21)$	-4764842	$-9*(8+(7^6*(5+4)-3)/2)+1$
-4695679	$9-8*(7^6*5-4*321)$	-4764844	$-9*(8+(7^6*(5+4)-3)/2)-1$
-4695697	$-9-8*(7^6*5-4*321)$	-4764869	$-9*(8+(7^6*(5+4)+3)/2)+1$
-4698727	$9-8*(7^6*5-43^2+1)$	-4764871	$-9*(8+(7^6*(5+4)+3)/2)-1$
-4698745	$-9-8*(7^6*5-43^2+1)$	-4776719	$-9^8(8-7+6)+5^4*(3^2+1)$
-4702487	$9-8*(7^6*5-432-1)$	-4777969	$-9^8(8-7+6)+5^4*(3^2-1)$
-4702503	$9-8*(7^6*5-432+1)$	-4780469	$-9^8(8-7+6)+5^4*(3+2-1)$
-4702505	$-9-8*(7^6*5-432-1)$	-4781085	$-9^8(8-7+6)+(5^4+3)^2+1$
-4702521	$-9-8*(7^6*5-432+1)$	-4781103	$-9^8(8-7+6)+(5^4-3)^2+1$
-4703351	$9-8*(7^6*5-4-321)$	-4784835	$-9^8(8-7+6)-(5^4-3)^2+1$
-4703369	$-9-8*(7^6*5-4-321)$	-4784853	$-9^8(8-7+6)-(5^4+3)^2+1$
-4703415	$9-8*(7^6*5+4-321)$	-4785469	$-9^8(8-7+6)-5^4*(3+2-1)$
-4703433	$-9-8*(7^6*5+4-321)$	-4787969	$-9^8(8-7+6)-5^4*(3^2-1)$
-4703783	$9-8*((7^6-54)*(3+2)-1)$	-4789219	$-9^8(8-7+6)-5^4*(3^2+1)$
-4703799	$9-8*((7^6-54)*(3+2)+1)$	-4806065	$(9+8*7/6)/(-5-4^3\wedge 2)^{-1}$
-4703817	$-9-8*((7^6-54)*(3+2)+1)$	-4823305	$98-(7^6-5)^*(43-2)+1$
-4704775	$9-8*(7^6*5-(4+3)*21)$	-4823307	$98-(7^6-5)^*(43-2)-1$
-4704793	$-9-8*(7^6*5-(4+3)*21)$	-4823501	$-98-(7^6-5)^*(43-2)+1$
-4704895	$9-8*(7^6*5-4*(32+1))$	-4823503	$-98-(7^6-5)^*(43-2)-1$
-4704913	$-9-8*(7^6*5-4*(32+1))$	-4823715	$98-(7^6+5)^*(43-2)+1$
-4704959	$9-8*(7^6*5-4*(32-1))$	-4823717	$98-(7^6+5)^*(43-2)-1$
-4704977	$-9-8*(7^6*5-4*(32-1))$	-4823911	$-98-(7^6+5)^*(43-2)+1$
-4705201	$-9-8*(7^6*5-4*(3+21))$	-4823913	$-98-(7^6+5)^*(43-2)-1$
-4705375	$9-8*(7^6*5+4*(3-21))$	-4844400	$-9*(8+7/(6/(5^4-3)))^2+1$
-4705393	$-9-8*(7^6*5+4*(3-21))$	-4844402	$-9*(8+7/(6/(5^4-3)))^2-1$
-4705479	$9-8*(7^6*5+4-3^2+1)$	-4875888	$9-(87+6)/5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-4705586	$9-8*(7^6*5-43)+21$	-4876008	$(9-876)^*(5^4*3^2-1)$
-4705603	$9-8*(7^6*5-43-2^2-1)$	-4877742	$(9-876)^*(5^4*3^2+1)$
-4705611	$9-8*(7^6*5-43+2^2-1)$	-4940535	$9-8*((7^6-5)/4-3)^2*21$
-4706287	$9-8*(7^6*5+43-2+1)$	-4940553	$-9-8*((7^6-5)/4-3)^2*21$
-4706299	$9-8*(7^6*5+43+2^2-1)$	-4940950	$98-(7^6-5)^*(43-2+1)$
-4706317	$-9-8*(7^6*5+43+2^2-1)$	-4940955	$9-8*((7^6+5)/4-3)^2*21$
-4706334	$-9-8*(7^6*5+43)-21$	-4940994	$-9-(8*(7^6-5)/4-3)^2*21$
-4706423	$9-8*(7^6*5-4+3^2+1)$	-4941081	$9+(8+7^6*(5-4-3))^2*21$
-4706527	$9-8*(7^6*5-4*(3-21))$	-4941102	$9-(8*(7^6-5)/4+3)^2*21$
-4706545	$-9-8*(7^6*5-4*(3-21))$	-4941146	$-98-(7^6-5)^*(43-2+1)$
-4706719	$9-8*(7^6*5+4*(3+21))$	-4941231	$(9+8*7^6*(5/4-3))^2*(2+1)$
-4706943	$9-8*(7^6*5+4*(32-1))$	-4941244	$-98*(7^6*(5+4)-3)/21$
-4706961	$-9-8*(7^6*5+4*(32-1))$	-4941272	$-98*(7^6*(5+4)+3)/21$
-4707007	$9-8*(7^6*5+4*(32+1))$	-4941285	$(-9+8*7^6*(5/4-3))^2*(2+1)$
-4707025	$-9-8*(7^6*5+4*(32+1))$	-4941370	$98-(7^6+5)^*(43-2+1)$
-4707127	$9-8*(7^6*5+(4+3)*21)$	-4941414	$-9-(8*(7^6+5)/4-3)^2*21$
-4707145	$-9-8*(7^6*5+(4+3)*21)$	-4941417	$9-(8-7^6*(5-4-3))^2*21$
-4708103	$9-8*((7^6+54)*(3+2)-1)$	-4941522	$9-(8*(7^6+5)/4+3)^2*21$
-4708119	$9-8*((7^6+54)*(3+2)+1)$	-4941543	$9-8*((7^6-5)/4+3)^2*21$
-4708487	$9-8*(7^6*5-4+321)$	-4941561	$-9-8*((7^6-5)/4+3)^2*21$
-4708505	$-9-8*(7^6*5-4+321)$	-4941566	$-98-(7^6+5)^*(43-2+1)$
-4708551	$9-8*(7^6*5+4+321)$	-4941963	$9-8*((7^6+5)/4+3)^2*21$
-4708569	$-9-8*(7^6*5+4+321)$	-4941981	$-9-8*((7^6+5)/4+3)^2*21$
-4709399	$9-8*(7^6*5+432-1)$	-4943943	$-9*((8*7^6+54^3)/2-1)$
-4709415	$9-8*(7^6*5+432+1)$	-4943961	$-9*((8*7^6+54^3)/2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-4976397	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5*(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-5291856	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3+2)+1)$
-4976883	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5*(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-5292836	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-4977240	$(-9-876)*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-5292838	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+(4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-4979010	$(-9-876)*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-5292849	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)+4*321$
-4999772	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-5292993	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)+4*321$
-4999887	$-9-8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-5293089	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4*(32+1))$
-5000057	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6*5-4+3)/2-1)$	-5293230	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)+43*21$
-5000159	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4+3)/2+1)$	-5293374	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)+43*21$
-5000197	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-5293494	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-43*2-1)$
-5000312	$-9-8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-5293725	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+43)+21$
-5000393	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-5293767	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+43)-21$
-5037839	$9*(8*7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*2+1$	-5293920	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4)+321$
-5037841	$9*(8*7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*2-1$	-5294021	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
-5039855	$-9*(8*7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*2+1$	-5294076	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4/3-21)$
-5039857	$9*(-8*7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))*2-1$	-5294077	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2)+1$
-5078014	$98-(7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	-5294333	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2)-1$
-5078040	$9*8-(7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	-5294389	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)-4^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
-5078066	$9*8-(7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	-5294490	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-4)-321$
-5078184	$-9*8-(7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	-5294643	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+43)+21$
-5078210	$-9*8-(7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	-5294685	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+43)-21$
-5078236	$-98-(7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	-5295036	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)-43*21$
-5117416	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-5295060	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+43*2+1)$
-5117531	$-9-8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-5295180	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)-43*21$
-5117612	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-5295393	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4*(32-1))$
-5117851	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-5295417	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)-4*321$
-5117950	$-9+8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-5295561	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)-4*321$
-5117966	$-9-8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-5295572	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-5118047	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-5295574	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+(4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-5176238	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2-1)$	-5295600	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+(4+3)*21)$
-5176434	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2-1)$	-5296716	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(3+2)+1)$
-5176678	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2-1)$	-5297058	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-4-321)$
-5176874	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2-1)$	-5297130	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4+321)$
-5227049	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3/21))$	-5297202	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4+321)$
-5228597	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-5298012	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-432-1)$
-5228741	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-5298030	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-432-1)$
-5228870	$(9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4))*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-5298156	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+432-1)$
-5235678	$9^{\wedge}8*76/(5^{\wedge}4-3/21)$	-5298174	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+432+1)$
-5243072	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)+4^{\wedge}3)/(2+1)$	-5302260	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-43*21)$
-5249475	$(9*8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	-5302404	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+43*21)$
-5250630	$(9+8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	-5305689	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-4*321)$
-5250810	$9+(8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	-5305833	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4*321)$
-5250828	$-9+(8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	-5306373	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3*21)$
-5250915	$9*8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3*21$	-5310517	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)-4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
-5251059	$-9*8-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3*21$	-5310661	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)-4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$
-5251146	$9-(8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	-5310765	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-43^{\wedge}2+1)$
-5251164	$-9-(8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*21$	-5310783	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-43^{\wedge}2-1)$
-5251344	$(9+8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*-21$	-5310909	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+43^{\wedge}2-1)$
-5252499	$(9*8+(7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3)*-21$	-5310927	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+43^{\wedge}2+1)$
-5257268	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-5330996	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-5257270	$-9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	-5330998	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-5257412	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-5331140	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-5257414	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	-5331142	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-5262153	$(9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5)*4)*-321$	-5333631	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4/3*2-1)$
-5277483	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+43^{\wedge}2+1)$	-5333665	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4/3*2+1)$
-5277501	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+43^{\wedge}2-1)$	-5342007	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-5277627	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-43^{\wedge}2-1)$	-5342025	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+43^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-5277645	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-43^{\wedge}2+1)$	-5359669	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-5277749	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	-5359813	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-5277893	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1)$	-5361505	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4/3/21))$
-5282037	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3*21)$	-5372703	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
-5282181	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3*21)$	-5372899	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-(5*4)^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$
-5282577	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+4*321)$	-5410658	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*321)$
-5282721	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4*321)$	-5411526	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2+1)$
-5286006	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+43*21)$	-5411722	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2+1)$
-5286150	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-43*21)$	-5411986	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2+1)$
-5290254	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+432-1)$	-5412182	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43+2+1)$
-5290380	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-432-1)$	-5418750	$(9-876)*5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-5290398	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-432+1)$	-5428644	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5/(4+3)+2)-1)$
-5291208	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+4+321)$	-5428678	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5/(4+3)+2)+1)$
-5291280	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-4+321)$	-5458208	$(-9/8)/(7*6*(5-4*3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-5291352	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4-321)$	-5504763	$9-(8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)-4*3)*21$
-5291838	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3+2)-1)$	-5504952	$9-(8^{\wedge}(7-(6-5)^{\wedge}4)-3)*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-5504970	$-9 \cdot (8^{\wedge}(7 - (6 - 5)^{\wedge}4) - 3) * 21$	-5772641	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) / 2 - 1)$
-5504987	$9 \cdot (8^{\wedge}(7 - 6 + 5) - 4 / 3) * 21$	-5772837	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) / 2 + 1)$
-5505061	$-9 \cdot (8^{\wedge}(7 - 6 + 5) + 4 / 3) * 21$	-5775238	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) / 2 - 1)$
-5505078	$9 \cdot (8^{\wedge}(7 - (6 - 5)^{\wedge}4) + 3) * 21$	-5775434	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) / 2 + 1)$
-5505267	$9 \cdot (8^{\wedge}(7 - 6 + 5) + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21$	-5780383	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3) / 2 - 1)$
-5505285	$-9 \cdot (8^{\wedge}(7 - 6 + 5) + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21$	-5780579	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3) / 2 + 1)$
-5526600	$-9 * (8 + 7) * ((6 - 5^{\wedge}4 / 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-5795181	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 - 3) / 2 - 1)$
-5526870	$-9 * (8 + 7) * ((6 - 5^{\wedge}4 / 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-5795377	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 - 3) / 2 + 1)$
-5531250	$(-9 - 876) * 5^{\wedge}4 * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-5795475	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 2 - 1)$
-5543700	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-5795671	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 2 + 1)$
-5543734	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-5856578	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) / 2 - 1)$
-5558040	$9 * (8 - ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 - 3) * 21)$	-5856774	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) / 2 + 1)$
-5558184	$-9 * (8 + ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 - 3) * 21)$	-5878670	$-98 / 7 - 6^{\wedge}(-5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21$
-5559174	$9 * (8 - ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 + 3) * 21)$	-5881199	$-9 * 87 / (65 * 4 / 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-5559318	$-9 * (8 + ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 + 3) * 21)$	-5881201	$-9 * 87 / (65 * 4 / 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-5617134	$(9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) / 2^{\wedge} - 1$	-5882270	$(9 * 8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * 5^{\wedge}4) * (3 / 2 + 1)$
-5617170	$(-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3) / 2^{\wedge} - 1$	-5882312	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4) * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-5646975	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4 - 3) - 21)$	-5882392	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4) * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-5647311	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4 - 3) + 21)$	-5882508	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4) * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-5664039	$9 - 87 / 6 * (5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3 / 2) - 1)$	-5882588	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4) * (3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-5664068	$9 - 87 / 6 * (5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3 / 2) + 1)$	-5882630	$(9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * 5^{\wedge}4) * (-3 / 2 - 1)$
-5664086	$-9 - 87 / 6 * (5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3 / 2) + 1)$	-5918103	$9^{\wedge}8 / -7 + (6 * 5)^{\wedge}4 / (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-5672828	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) / 2 - 1)$	-5968173	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 - 2 - 1)$
-5700860	$9 * (8 - (7 + 6)^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$	-5968207	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 - 2 + 1)$
-5700862	$9 * (8 - (7 + 6)^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$	-5968241	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 + 2 - 1)$
-5701004	$-9 * (8 + (7 + 6)^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$	-5968275	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 + 2 + 1)$
-5701006	$-9 * (8 + (7 + 6)^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$	-5974272	$9 * 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 321)$
-5733931	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 - 3) / 2 - 1)$	-5996988	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 - 21)$
-5734127	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 - 3) / 2 + 1)$	-5997039	$(9 + 8) * (-7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * (2 + 1)$
-5734225	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 2 - 1)$	-5997702	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 + 21)$
-5734421	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 2 + 1)$	-5999062	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 - 2 + 1)$
-5749023	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3) / 2 - 1)$	-5999096	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 + 2 - 1)$
-5749219	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3) / 2 + 1)$	-5999130	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 + 2 + 1)$
-5754168	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 43) / 2 - 1)$	-5999589	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 3 - 2 - 1)$
-5754364	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 43) / 2 + 1)$	-5999623	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 3 - 2 + 1)$
-5756765	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) / 2 - 1)$	-5999657	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 3 + 2 - 1)$
-5756961	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) / 2 + 1)$	-5999827	$(9 + 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (-4 + 3 - 2) + 1)$
-5761322	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4^{\wedge}3) / 2 - 1)$	-5999861	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 - 3 + 2) + 1)$
-5761763	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3) / 2 - 1)$	-5999883	$(9 * 8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3)) * (2 + 1)$
-5761812	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}3) / 2 - 1)$	-6000167	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * 3 + 2 - 1)$
-5761959	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4^{\wedge}3) / 2 + 1)$	-6000315	$(9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5^{\wedge}4 - 3)) * (-2 - 1)$
-5762204	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 2 - 1)$	-6000337	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 - 3 + 2) - 1)$
-5762351	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 43) / 2 - 1)$	-6000371	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 - 3 + 2) + 1)$
-5762400	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 2 + 1)$	-6000541	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * 3 - 2 + 1)$
-5762547	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 43) / 2 + 1)$	-6000575	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * 3 + 2 - 1)$
-5762841	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 43) / 2 - 1)$	-6000609	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * 3 + 2 + 1)$
-5762988	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * (4 + 3)) / 2 - 1)$	-6001068	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 - 2 - 1)$
-5763037	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 43) / 2 + 1)$	-6001102	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 - 2 + 1)$
-5763184	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * (4 + 3)) / 2 + 1)$	-6001136	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 + 2 - 1)$
-5763380	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - (5 + 4) * 3) / 2 - 1)$	-6002496	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 - 21)$
-5763576	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4 - 3) / 2 - 1)$	-6003159	$(9 + 8) * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) * (-2 - 1)$
-5763772	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4 - 3) / 2 + 1)$	-6003210	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 + 21)$
-5764017	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4 / 3) / 2 + 1)$	-6027792	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * (2 + 1)$
-5765585	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 / 3) / 2 - 1)$	-6029191	$98 + (7 - 6^{\wedge}5) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-5765830	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 2 - 1)$	-6029217	$9 * 8 + (7 - 6^{\wedge}5) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-5766026	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 2 + 1)$	-6029237	$98 + (7 - 6^{\wedge}5) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-5766222	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + (5 + 4) * 3) / 2 + 1)$	-6029263	$9 * 8 + (7 - 6^{\wedge}5) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-5766418	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * (4 + 3)) / 2 - 1)$	-6029361	$-9 * 8 + (7 - 6^{\wedge}5) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-5766565	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 43) / 2 - 1)$	-6029407	$-9 * 8 + (7 - 6^{\wedge}5) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-5766614	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * (4 + 3)) / 2 + 1)$	-6031923	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 - 2 - 1)$
-5766761	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 43) / 2 + 1)$	-6031957	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 - 2 + 1)$
-5767055	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 43) / 2 - 1)$	-6031991	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 + 2 - 1)$
-5767137	$9 \cdot (87 - 65) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-6032025	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 3 + 2 + 1)$
-5767199	$-9 \cdot (87 - 65) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-6050331	$-9 * (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 / (4 + 3) - 21)$
-5767202	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 - 3) / 2 - 1)$	-6081755	$9 \cdot (8 + 76 / 5) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-5767251	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 43) / 2 + 1)$	-6081773	$-9 \cdot (8 + 76 / 5) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-5767398	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 - 3) / 2 + 1)$	-6093684	$-9^{\wedge}(8 - 7 + 6) - 5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-5767496	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 + 3) / 2 - 1)$	-6093694	$-9^{\wedge}(8 - 7 + 6) - 5^{\wedge}(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-5767643	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) / 2 - 1)$	-6111071	$-9 * (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-5767790	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge}3) / 2 + 1)$	-6111073	$-9 * (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-5767839	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * 3) / 2 + 1)$	-6111791	$-9 * (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-5768280	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge}3) / 2 + 1)$	-6111793	$-9 * (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-6137586	$(9-87)*(6*5^4-3)*21$	-6469903	$(9*8-7^6*5)*(4*3-2+1)$
-6142033	$9^8/-7+(6+5^4)/21$	-6471487	$(9*8+7^6*5)*(-4-3*2-1)$
-6147311	$9^8/-7+(6^5-4)/(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-6578543	$(9-8*7)*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)/2+1)$
-6147414	$(9-87)*(6*5^4+3)*21$	-6585131	$(9-8*(7^6-5^4)/3)*21$
-6149463	$9^8/-7-6*5/((4/3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$	-6585509	$(-9-8*(7^6-5^4)/3)*21$
-6149493	$9^8/-7+6*5/((4/3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$	-6588223	$9-8*((7^6-5)^*(4+3)+21)$
-6149516	$9^8/-7+(6*5^4+3)/21$	-6588241	$-9-8*((7^6-5)^*(4+3)+21)$
-6149593	$9^8/-7-6*5^4/21$	-6588447	$9-8*((7^6+5)^*(4+3)-21)$
-6150603	$9^8/-7-6/5^{\wedge}-4/(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-6591179	$(9-8*(7^6+5^4)/3)*21$
-6151383	$9^8/-7-6^5/(4+(3+2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-6591557	$(-9-8*(7^6+5^4)/3)*21$
-6156703	$-98*((7^6+(5*4)^3)/2-1)$	-6639894	$(9+8)*(7*6-5^4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-6156899	$-98*((7^6+(5*4)^3)/2+1)$	-6639928	$(9+8)*7*6-5^4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-6157431	$9^8/-7+6^5/(4^{\wedge}-3-2+1)$	-6641322	$(-9-8)*(7*6+5^4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-6201600	$-9*(8+7)*((6+5^4/3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$	-6641356	$(-9-8)*7*6+5^4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-6201870	$-9*(8+7)*((6+5^4/3)^{\wedge}+2+1)$	-6656299	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2-1)$
-6336167	$9*8-7^6*(54-3/21)$	-6656333	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^{\wedge}(4+3))^*2+1)$
-6336222	$9+8-7^6*(54-3/21)$	-6665103	$9*(-8*7^6+5^4*321)$
-6336238	$9-8-7^6*(54-3/21)$	-6666805	$(-9-8)*((7^6*5+4)/3*2-1)$
-6336240	$-9+8-7^6*(54-3/21)$	-6666839	$(-9-8)*((7^6*5+4)/3*2+1)$
-6336256	$-9-8-7^6*(54-3/21)$	-6693994	$-9-(8/(7+65^4*3-2))^{\wedge}-1$
-6336311	$-9*8-7^6*(54-3/21)$	-6750135	$-9/8*(7^6*(54-3)+21)$
-6342709	$9*(8-7^6*5)-4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$	-6821241	$9+(8-7*6)*5^4*321$
-6342853	$-9*(8+7^6*5)-4^{\wedge}(3^2+1)$	-6821259	$-9+(8-7*6)*5^4*321$
-6349977	$9*((8-(7^6-5^4)*3)*2+1)$	-6902038	$(9/((8-7^{\wedge}-6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-6349995	$9*((8-(7^6-5^4)*3)*2-1)$	-6906357	$-9*(876^{\wedge}(-5+4+3)-2-1)$
-6350049	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4)*3*2+1)$	-6940898	$98+(7^6-5)^*(4-3*21)$
-6350193	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*3*2-1)$	-6941094	$-98+(7^6-5)^*(4-3*21)$
-6350211	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*3*2+1)$	-6941172	$98+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+21$
-6350265	$-9*((8+(7^6-5^4)*3)*2-1)$	-6941214	$98+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-21$
-6351821	$9*(8-(7^6-5*4)*3)*2+1$	-6941368	$-98+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+21$
-6351823	$9*(8-(7^6-5*4)*3)*2-1$	-6941410	$-98+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-21$
-6351893	$9*(8-(7^6-5*4)*3*2)+1$	-6941488	$98+(7^6+5)^*(4-3*21)$
-6351895	$9*(8-(7^6-5*4)*3*2)-1$	-6941684	$-98+(7^6+5)^*(4-3*21)$
-6352037	$-9*(8+(7^6-5*4)*3*2)+1$	-6945562	$(9^8-7^6*5^4)/3+21$
-6352039	$-9*(8+(7^6-5*4)*3*2)-1$	-6986224	$-98*((7/(6-5^4*3))^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-6352109	$9*(-8-(7^6-5*4)*3)*2+1$	-6999801	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)^*(4+3)/2-1)$
-6352111	$9*(-8-(7^6-5*4)*3)*2-1$	-6999835	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)^*(4+3)/2+1)$
-6352487	$9*(8-(7^6-5-4)*3*2)+1$	-7000073	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}(6+5-4)-3)/2-1)$
-6352489	$9*(8-(7^6-5-4)*3*2)-1$	-7000107	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}(6+5-4)-3)/2+1)$
-6352533	$(9-8*(7^6-5)/4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-7000124	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}(6+5-4)+3)/2-1)$
-6352752	$(98-7^6*5^4/3)^*(2+1)$	-7000158	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}(6+5-4)+3)/2+1)$
-6353340	$(98+7^6*5^4/3)^*(-2-1)$	-7000396	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5)^*(4+3)/2-1)$
-6353559	$(-9-8*(7^6+5)/4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-7000430	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5)^*(4+3)/2+1)$
-6353603	$-9*(8+(7^6+5+4)*3*2)+1$	-7030719	$9*(8*(-7^6+5^4*3^2)+1)$
-6353605	$-9*(8+(7^6+5+4)*3*2)-1$	-7058897	$9*((8-7^6*5^4)/3+2)+1$
-6353981	$9*(8-(7^6+5*4)*3)*2+1$	-7058899	$9*((8-7^6*5^4)/3+2)-1$
-6353983	$9*(8-(7^6+5*4)*3)*2-1$	-7058981	$-9*((8+7^6*5^4)/3+2)+1$
-6354053	$9*(8-(7^6+5*4)*3*2)+1$	-7058983	$-9*((8+7^6*5^4)/3+2)-1$
-6354055	$9*(8-(7^6+5*4)*3*2)-1$	-7059105	$9*((8-7^6*5^4)/3-21)$
-6354197	$-9*(8+(7^6+5*4)*3*2)+1$	-7059201	$-9*(8+7^6*5^4/3+21)$
-6354199	$-9*(8+(7^6+5*4)*3*2)-1$	-7076224	$-98*((7/(6+5^4*3))^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-6354269	$9*(-8-(7^6+5*4)*3)*2+1$	-7076420	$-98*((7/(6+5^4*3))^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-6354271	$9*(-8-(7^6+5*4)*3)*2-1$	-7077591	$-9*((8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)-4)*3-21)$
-6355809	$9*((8-(7^6+5^4)*3)*2+1)$	-7077869	$9*(8^{\wedge}(7-(6-5)^{\wedge}4)*-3+2)+1$
-6355827	$9*((8-(7^6+5^4)*3)*2-1)$	-7077907	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(7-(6-5)^{\wedge}4)*3+2)-1$
-6356025	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3*2-1)$	-7078185	$-9*((8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)+4)*3+21)$
-6356043	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3*2+1)$	-7098157	$(-9/(8+7^6*5^4-2))^{\wedge}-1$
-6369781	$9*8-7^6*(54+3/21)$	-7138232	$(9+8)*7-(6^5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-6369836	$9+8-7^6*(54+3/21)$	-7138266	$(9+8)*7-(6^5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-6369852	$9-8-7^6*(54+3/21)$	-7138470	$(-9-8)*7+(6^5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-6369854	$-9+8-7^6*(54+3/21)$	-7138504	$(-9-8)*7+(6^5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-6369870	$-9-8-7^6*(54+3/21)$	-7147197	$-9/8*(7^6*5^4-3+21)$
-6369925	$-9*8-7^6*(54+3/21)$	-7147287	$(98+7^6*5^4)/(3^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-6386723	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4)*3*2)+1$	-7166800	$-98*((7/(6+5^4)/3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-6386725	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4)*3*2)-1$	-7171983	$(-98+7)*6*5^4+3)*21$
-6386867	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3*2)+1$	-7176186	$98-(7^6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-6386869	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3*2)-1$	-7176212	$9*8-(7^6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-6405280	$-98*((7^6*5+4)/3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-7176356	$-9*8-(7^6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-6405476	$-98*((7^6*5+4)/3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-7176382	$-98-(7^6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-6456379	$(-9-8)*(7^6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-7176796	$98-(7^6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-6456413	$(-9-8)*(7^6-5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-7176822	$9*8-(7^6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-6456549	$(-9-8)*(7^6+5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-7176966	$-9*8-(7^6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-7176992	$-98 - (7^6+5) * (4^3-2-1)$	-7471101	$-9*8 - (7^6+5) * (4^3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-7293919	$9-8*(7^6-5)/4*(32-1)$	-7471127	$-98 - (7^6+5) * (4^3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-7293937	$-9-8*(7^6-5)/4*(32-1)$	-7526071	$9-8*(7^6-54) * (3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-7294539	$9-8*(7^6+5)/4*(32-1)$	-7526089	$-9-8*(7^6-54) * (3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-7300648	$9-(8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4*3) * 21$	-7529095	$9-(8*7^6-54) * (3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-7300666	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4*3) * 21$	-7529097	$98-(7^6-5) * 4^{\wedge}3+21$
-7335648	$9-(8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4/3) * 21$	-7529113	$-9-(8*7^6-54) * (3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-7335666	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7/6-5^{\wedge}4/3) * 21$	-7529888	$9*(8*(7^6+5)+4) * (3^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-7370454	$(98-(7^6-5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	-7529959	$9-(8*7^6+54) * (3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-7372335	$9+(8-(7^6-5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	-7529975	$-98-(7^6+5) * 4^{\wedge}3-21$
-7372353	$-9+(8-(7^6-5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	-7529977	$-9-(8*7^6+54) * (3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-7372414	$98-(7^6-5^{\wedge}4) * 3 * 21$	-7530816	$9*8*(7^6+5*4) * (3^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-7372610	$-98-(7^6-5^{\wedge}4) * 3 * 21$	-7532983	$9-8*(7^6+54) * (3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-7372671	$9-(8+(7^6-5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	-7533001	$-9-8*(7^6+54) * (3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-7372689	$-9-(8+(7^6-5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	-7553952	$(9+87) * (-6*5^{\wedge}4+3) * 21$
-7374570	$(98+(7^6-5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * -21$	-7566048	$(9+87) * (-6*5^{\wedge}4-3) * 21$
-7379398	$9-(8^{\wedge}7/6+5^{\wedge}4*3) * 21$	-7567991	$9-(876+5^{\wedge}4*3) * 21$
-7379416	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7/6+5^{\wedge}4*3) * 21$	-7567992	$9-(876+5^{\wedge}4*3) * 21$
-7383366	$-9*876*(5^{\wedge}4*3/2-1)$	-7567993	$9-(876+5^{\wedge}4*3) * 21$
-7399134	$-9*876*(5^{\wedge}4*3/2+1)$	-7568009	$-9-(876+5^{\wedge}4*3) * 21$
-7408128	$(9+8-(7^6-54) * 3) * 21$	-7568010	$-9-(876+5^{\wedge}4*3) * 21$
-7408308	$9+(8-(7^6-54) * 3) * 21$	-7568011	$-9-(876+5^{\wedge}4*3) * 21$
-7408326	$-9+(8-(7^6-54) * 3) * 21$	-7581520	$-98*((7/(6^{\wedge}5/4+3))^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-7408464	$(9-8-(7^6-54) * 3) * 21$	-7581716	$-98*((7/(6^{\wedge}5/4+3))^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-7408506	$(9-8+(7^6-54) * 3) * -21$	-7587940	$98-(7^6-5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-7408569	$(98-(7^6-5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	-7587966	$9*8-(7^6-5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-7408644	$9-(8+(7^6-54) * 3) * 21$	-7588110	$-9*8-(7^6-5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-7408662	$-9-(8+(7^6-54) * 3) * 21$	-7588136	$-98-(7^6-5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-7408842	$(9+8+(7^6-54) * 3) * -21$	-7588611	$9*8-(7^6+5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-7409262	$(98-(7^6-5-4) * 3) * 21$	-7588755	$-9*8-(7^6+5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-7409766	$(98-(7^6-5+4) * 3) * 21$	-7588781	$-98-(7^6+5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-7409892	$(98-(7^6+5-4) * 3) * 21$	-7623785	$(9*8-7^6/5) * (4+321)$
-7410396	$(98-(7^6+5+4) * 3) * 21$	-7641660	$(9+8-7^6/5) * (4+321)$
-7410450	$9+(8-(7^6-5*4) * 3) * 21$	-7644576	$9+(8-7^6/5) * (4+321)$
-7410786	$9-(8+(7^6-5*4) * 3) * 21$	-7644594	$-9+(8-7^6/5) * (4+321)$
-7411143	$9+(8-(7^6-5-4) * 3) * 21$	-7645470	$-98*((7^6-5^{\wedge}4)/3 * 2-1)$
-7411161	$-9+(8-(7^6-5-4) * 3) * 21$	-7645666	$-98*((7^6-5^{\wedge}4)/3 * 2+1)$
-7411474	$98-(7^6-5) * (4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	-7646762	$98-(7^6-5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
-7411773	$9+(8-(7^6+5-4) * 3) * 21$	-7646788	$9*8-(7^6-5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
-7412300	$-98-(7^6+5) * (4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	-7646932	$-9*8-(7^6-5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
-7412613	$9-(8+(7^6+5+4) * 3) * 21$	-7646958	$-98-(7^6-5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
-7412970	$9+(8-(7^6+5*4) * 3) * 21$	-7647412	$98-(7^6+5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
-7413306	$9-(8+(7^6+5*4) * 3) * 21$	-7647438	$9*8-(7^6+5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
-7413378	$(98+(7^6-5-4) * 3) * -21$	-7647582	$-9*8-(7^6+5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
-7413882	$(98+(7^6-5+4) * 3) * -21$	-7647608	$-98-(7^6+5) * (4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
-7414008	$(98+(7^6+5-4) * 3) * -21$	-7649776	$9-(8+7^6/5) * (4+321)$
-7414512	$(98+(7^6+5+4) * 3) * -21$	-7649794	$-9-(8+7^6/5) * (4+321)$
-7414932	$(9+8-(7^6+54) * 3) * 21$	-7652710	$(9+8+7^6/5) * (-4-321)$
-7415112	$9+(8-(7^6+54) * 3) * 21$	-7653428	$9*(8-7^6*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-7415130	$-9+(8-(7^6+54) * 3) * 21$	-7653430	$9*(8-7^6*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-7415205	$(98+(7^6+5*4) * 3) * -21$	-7653572	$-9*(8+7^6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-7415268	$(9-8-(7^6+54) * 3) * 21$	-7653574	$-9*(8+7^6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-7415310	$(9-8+(7^6+54) * 3) * -21$	-7670585	$(9*8+7^6/5) * (-4-321)$
-7415448	$9-(8+(7^6+54) * 3) * 21$	-7670852	$98*(-7^6+5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$
-7415466	$-9-(8+(7^6+54) * 3) * 21$	-7686385	$-98*((7^6+5/4)/3 * 2-1)$
-7415646	$(9+8+(7^6+54) * 3) * -21$	-7686581	$-98*((7^6+5/4)/3 * 2+1)$
-7449204	$(98-(7^6+5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	-7687610	$-98*((7^6+5*4)/3 * 2-1)$
-7451085	$9+(8-(7^6+5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	-7703094	$-98*7*(6/5^{\wedge}-4*3-21)$
-7451103	$-9+(8-(7^6+5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	-7731906	$-98*7*(6/5^{\wedge}-4*3+21)$
-7451164	$98-(7^6+5^{\wedge}4) * 3 * 21$	-7746606	$-98*((7^6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
-7451360	$-98-(7^6+5^{\wedge}4) * 3 * 21$	-7746802	$-98*((7^6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}2+1)$
-7451421	$9-(8+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	-7764495	$9-8*(7^6-5)/4*(32+1)$
-7451439	$-9-(8+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * 21$	-7764513	$-9-8*(7^6-5)/4*(32+1)$
-7453320	$(98+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4) * 3) * -21$	-7764736	$98-7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-7469964	$9*(8-(7^6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}21)$	-7764932	$-98-7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-7470108	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^{\wedge}(4+3))^{\wedge}21)$	-7765155	$9-8*(7^6+5)/4*(32+1)$
-7470296	$98-(7^6-5) * (4^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-7765173	$-9-8*(7^6+5)/4*(32+1)$
-7470322	$9*8-(7^6-5) * (4^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-7808949	$9/8*(7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2+1)$
-7470466	$-9*8-(7^6-5) * (4^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-7825627	$(9+8) * (7^6*5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-7470492	$-98-(7^6-5) * (4^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-7863786	$9*8*7-6*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-7470931	$98-(7^6+5) * (4^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-7863810	$9*8*7-6*(5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-7470957	$9*8-(7^6+5) * (4^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-7863822	$9*8*7-6*(5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-7863846	$9*8^7-6*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-8290719	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$
-7864155	$9*(8+7)-6*5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-8290737	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$
-7864179	$9*(8+7)-6*(5^*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-8296353	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
-7864191	$9*(8+7)-6*(5^*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-8335539	$9*(8*(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)+21)$
-7864449	$-9*(8+7)-6*(5^*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-8335709	$9*(8*(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)+2)+1$
-7864461	$-9*(8+7)-6*(5^*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-8335711	$9*(8*(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)+2)-1$
-7864485	$-9*(8+7)-6*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-8335745	$9*(8*(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)-2)+1$
-7864794	$9*8^*-7-6*5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-8335747	$9*(8*(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)-2)-1$
-7864818	$9*8^*-7-6*(5^*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-8335917	$9*(8*(-7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)-21)$
-7864830	$9*8^*-7-6*(5^*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-8352036	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)*21)$
-7864854	$9*8^*-7-6*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-8353170	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*21)$
-7882050	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4+3*21)$	-8369478	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3-21))$
-7882220	$-9*8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^3+2+1)$	-8431388	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*43/(2+1)$
-7882246	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4+3*21)$	-8431500	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*43)/(2+1)$
-7882720	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+3*21)$	-8431518	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*43)/(2+1)$
-7882890	$-9*8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^3+2+1)$	-8436977	$9*(-8/7^{\wedge}-6+5^{\wedge}4*3^*2)+1$
-7882916	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+3*21)$	-8436979	$9*(-8/7^{\wedge}-6+5^{\wedge}4*3^*2)-1$
-7994335	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-321)$	-8453664	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$
-7995015	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-321)$	-8455539	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)-21)$
-7999333	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-8455709	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)-2)+1$
-7999622	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*-4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-8455711	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)-2)-1$
-7999656	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*-4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-8455745	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)+2)+1$
-7999673	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3^*2-1)$	-8455747	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)+2)-1$
-7999724	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*-4+3+2-1)$	-8455917	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)+21)$
-7999758	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3+2-1)$	-8459423	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2)+1$
-7999826	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3-2+1)$	-8459425	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2)-1$
-7999860	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3+2-1)$	-8459531	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*2)+1$
-7999911	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3^*2+1)$	-8459533	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*2)-1$
-7999962	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-8468151	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-321)$
-8000013	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-8468169	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-321)$
-8000060	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^3-2+1)$	-8468664	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3+21)$
-8000204	$-9*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^3-2+1)$	-8469042	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3-21)$
-8000230	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^3-2+1)$	-8470527	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3-21)$
-8000251	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-8470929	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3+21)$
-8000302	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*-4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-8472414	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3-21)$
-8000353	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3^*2-1)$	-8472792	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3+21)$
-8000404	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3-2+1)$	-8473287	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+321)$
-8000438	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3+2-1)$	-8473305	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+321)$
-8000506	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3-2+1)$	-8481923	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*2)+1$
-8000540	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3+2-1)$	-8481925	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*2)-1$
-8000591	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3^*2+1)$	-8482031	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2)+1$
-8000608	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-8482033	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2)-1$
-8000642	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-8485539	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)-21)$
-8000931	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-8485709	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)-2)+1$
-8005249	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+321)$	-8485711	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)-2)-1$
-8005929	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+321)$	-8485745	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)+2)+1$
-8031933	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6)^*5^{\wedge}4+3)*21$	-8485747	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)+2)-1$
-8033067	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6)^*5^{\wedge}4-3)*21$	-8485917	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)+21)$
-8116353	$9*(-8/7^{\wedge}-6+5^{\wedge}4*3^*21)$	-8487792	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$
-8117565	$(9*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3))*(2+1)$	-8504477	$-9*(8/7^{\wedge}-6+5^{\wedge}4*3^*2)+1$
-8117662	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^3)+21$	-8504479	$-9*(8/7^{\wedge}-6+5^{\wedge}4*3^*2)-1$
-8117704	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^3)-21$	-8521077	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^3/21))$
-8117858	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^3)+21$	-8521221	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^3/21))$
-8117900	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^3)-21$	-8571978	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3-21))$
-8117997	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3))*(-2-1)$	-8588286	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*21)$
-8130854	$(-9/(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$	-8589420	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)*21)$
-8158130	$(-9-8)/7/(6^{\wedge}(5+4)/3-2)^{\wedge}-1$	-8605539	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)-21)$
-8170071	$(-9/(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4+3^*2))^{\wedge}-1$	-8605709	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)-2)+1$
-8170622	$(9-(8+7^{\wedge}6)*5^{\wedge}4/3)/(2+1)$	-8605711	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)-2)-1$
-8170628	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6)*5^{\wedge}4/3)/(-2-1)$	-8605745	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)+2)+1$
-8205597	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(32-1))$	-8605747	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)+2)-1$
-8205741	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*(32-1))$	-8605917	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)+21)$
-8233372	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4+3)-21)$	-8640641	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-8235136	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4+3)-2-1)$	-8640675	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-8235178	$(9*8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-8644776	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*3-21)$
-8235381	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-8645103	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
-8235479	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-8645511	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4^*3-21)$
-8235682	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)*(-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-8646785	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-8237488	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4+3)+21)$	-8646883	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-8262135	$(-98-7)*6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)*21$	-8647520	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4^*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-8275365	$(-98-7)*(6*5^{\wedge}4+3)*21$	-8648892	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*3+21)$
-8285103	$9*(-8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$	-8649627	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4^*3+21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-8656353	$-9*(8*7^6+5^4*(32+1))$	-9417819	$(9*8-(7^6-5)/4)*321$
-8734995	$9*(8-(7^6-5)/4*(32+1))$	-9429093	$(9-8*7)*(-6+5^4*321)$
-8735139	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)/4*(32+1))$	-9429657	$(9-8*7)*(6+5^4*321)$
-8792307	$-9*87*(6/5^4-4*3-21)$	-9435474	$(9+8-(7^6-5)/4)*321$
-8817201	$9*(87-6^4(5+4-3)*21)$	-9438372	$-9+(8-(7^6-5)/4)*321$
-8818767	$-9*(87+6^4(5+4-3)*21)$	-9440610	$(9-8-(7^6-5)/4)*321$
-8822595	$(9*8-7^6*5)*(4*3+2+1)$	-9440859	$9*8-(7^6-5)/4*321$
-8823577	$98+7^6*((5-43)*2+1)$	-9440914	$9+8-(7^6-5)/4*321$
-8824755	$(9*-8-7^6*5)*(4*3+2+1)$	-9440930	$9-8-(7^6-5)/4*321$
-8825103	$-9*(8/7^6-6+5^4*3*21)$	-9440932	$-9+8-(7^6-5)/4*321$
-8825193	$-9*87*(6/5^4-4*3+21)$	-9440948	$-9-8-(7^6-5)/4*321$
-8886053	$(-9-8)*(7^6*5-4^4(3^2-1))$	-9441003	$-9*8-(7^6-5)/4*321$
-8964648	$-98*7*(6+(5^4-3)*21)$	-9441252	$(9-8+(7^6-5)/4)*-321$
-8982008	$-9*(876-5^4*3)^2+1$	-9443490	$9-(8+(7^6-5)/4)*321$
-8982010	$-9*(876-5^4*3)^2-1$	-9443508	$-9-(8+(7^6-5)/4)*321$
-9000106	$(-9-8)*((7^6*5+4)-3)/2-1$	-9446388	$(9+8+(7^6-5)/4)*-321$
-9000140	$(-9-8)*((7^6*5+4)-3)/2+1$	-9464043	$(9*8+(7^6-5)/4)*-321$
-9000157	$(-9-8)*((7^6*5+4)+3)/2-1$	-9508352	$-98*(7^6-5^4*(32+1))$
-9000191	$(-9-8)*((7^6*5+4)+3)/2+1$	-9517688	$(9+8)*(7-6^4(-5+4*3)*2+1)$
-9042852	$98*7*(6-(5^4+3)*21)$	-9517722	$(9+8)*(7-6^4(-5+4*3)*2-1)$
-9043897	$9*(8+(7/6-5)*4^3)^2-1$	-9517926	$(-9-8)*(7+6^4(-5+4*3)*2-1)$
-9044039	$9*(-8+(7/6-5)*4^3)^2+1$	-9517960	$(-9-8)*(7+6^4(-5+4*3)*2+1)$
-9044041	$9*(-8+(7/6-5)*4^3)^2-1$	-9525114	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4)*3^2+1)$
-9051084	$-98*7*(6+(5^4+3)*21)$	-9525132	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4)*3^2-1)$
-9056915	$(98-7^6*(5-4/3))^2+1$	-9525258	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*3^2-1)$
-9058796	$9+(8-7^6*(5-4/3))^2+1$	-9525276	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*3^2+1)$
-9058814	$-9+(8-7^6*(5-4/3))^2-1$	-9526320	$9*((8-7^6/5)*(43+2)+1)$
-9058875	$98-7^6*(5-4/3)*21$	-9526338	$9*((8-7^6/5)*(43+2)-1)$
-9059071	$-98-7^6*(5-4/3)*21$	-9527876	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4)/3^2-2)+1$
-9059132	$9-(8+7^6*(5-4/3))^2+1$	-9527878	$9*(8-(7^6-5^4)/3^2-2)-1$
-9059150	$-9-(8+7^6*(5-4/3))^2-1$	-9528020	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*3^2)+1$
-9061031	$(98+7^6*(5-4/3))^2-1$	-9528022	$-9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*3^2)-1$
-9129050	$98-(7/(6-(5^4)^3)^2)^2-1$	-9529074	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+4)-3*21)$
-9129076	$9*(-8+(7/(6-(5^4)^3)^2)^2)^2-1$	-9529176	$9*(8-7^6*(5+4))+321$
-9129220	$9*-8-(7/(6-(5^4)^3)^2)^2-1$	-9529320	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+4))+321$
-9129246	$-98-(7/(6-(5^4)^3)^2)^2-1$	-9529344	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+4)-32-1)$
-9168785	$-9*((8-765)*4/3)^2-1$	-9529442	$9*(8-7^6*(5+4)+3*2)+1$
-9174893	$98+7*(6-5*4^3)^2+1$	-9529444	$9*(8-7^6*(5+4)+3*2)-1$
-9174907	$98+7*(6-5*4^3)^2-1$	-9529550	$9*(8-7^6*(5+4)-3*2)+1$
-9174935	$98+7*(6-5*(4^3)^2+1)$	-9529588	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+4)-3*2)-1$
-9174949	$98-7*(6+5*(4^3)^2-1)$	-9529694	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+4)+3*2)+1$
-9174977	$98-7*(6+5*4^3)^2-1$	-9529696	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+4)+3*2)-1$
-9175131	$-98+7*(6-5*(4^3)^2+1)$	-9529818	$9*(8-7^6*(5+4))-321$
-9176549	$9*(8-7^6*(5^4/3+2))+1$	-9529857	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+4)+3+21)$
-9176551	$9*(8-7^6*(5^4/3+2))-1$	-9529962	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+4))-321$
-9176693	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4/3+2))+1$	-9531116	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4)/3^2-2)+1$
-9176695	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4/3+2))-1$	-9531118	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4)/3^2-2)-1$
-9223662	$98*(7^6/5^4+3+2)^2-1$	-9531260	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3^2)+1$
-9359532	$(9-87)*6*(5^4*32-1)$	-9531262	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3^2)-1$
-9360468	$(9-87)*6*(5^4*32+1)$	-9532800	$-9*((8+7^6/5)*(43+2)-1)$
-9397215	$9/8*(7^6*(5-4^3-2))-1$	-9532818	$-9*((8+7^6/5)*(43+2)+1)$
-9407591	$9-8*(7^6-5^4)*(3^2+1)$	-9533862	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4)*3^2+1)$
-9407609	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4)*(3^2+1)$	-9533880	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4)*3^2-1)$
-9411231	$9-8*((7^6*5-43)*2+1)$	-9534006	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3^2-1)$
-9411371	$9-(8*7^6-5^4)*(3^2+1)$	-9534024	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*3^2+1)$
-9411389	$-9-(8*7^6-5^4)*(3^2+1)$	-9629935	$9+8*(7-6*5^4*321)$
-9411632	$(9*8-7^6*5^4)*(3+2-1)$	-9629953	$-9+8*(7-6*5^4*321)$
-9411710	$(9-8*(7^6*5-4^3))/2^2-1$	-9630047	$9-8*(7+6*5^4*321)$
-9411746	$(-9-8*(7^6*5-4^3))^2/1$	-9630852	$-98*(7^6-5^4*(32-1))$
-9411756	$(9+(8-7^6*5)^4)*(3+2-1)$	-9699193	$98-(7^6-5)*(4^3)^2-1$
-9411874	$(-9-8*(7^6*5-4))/3(2-1)$	-9699219	$9*8-(7^6-5)*(4^3)^2-1$
-9411966	$(9-8*(7^6*5+4))/3(2-1)$	-9699267	$98-(7^6-5)*(4^3)^2+1$
-9412084	$(9+(8+7^6*5)^4)*(-3-2+1)$	-9699293	$9*8-(7^6-5)*(4^3)^2+1$
-9412094	$(9-8*(7^6*5+4^3))/2^2-1$	-9699363	$9*-8-(7^6-5)*(4^3)^2-1$
-9412130	$(-9-8*(7^6*5+4^3))^2/1$	-9699437	$9*-8-(7+6*5)*(4^3)^2+1$
-9412208	$(9*8+7^6*5^4)*(-3-2+1)$	-9721637	$(-9-8)*(7^6*5-4^4(3^2+1))$
-9412451	$9-(8*7^6+5^4)*(3^2+1)$	-9799812	$-9*876*((5^4-3)*2-1)$
-9412469	$-9-(8*7^6+5^4)*(3^2+1)$	-9804223	$(9-8*(7-6/5))*(4^3)^2+1$
-9412607	$9-8*((7^6*5+43)*2+1)$	-9815580	$-9*876*((5^4-3)*2+1)$
-9412609	$-9-8*((7^6*5+43)*2-1)$	-9875852	$-98*(7^6-5^4*3^2(2+1))$
-9416231	$9-8*(7^6+5^4)*(3^2+1)$	-9880458	$(98-7^6*(5-4+3))^2+1$
-9416249	$-9-8*(7^6+5^4)*(3^2+1)$	-9881856	$9+(8-(7^6-5)*4+3)*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-9881982	$9+(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3)^*21$	-10002001	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5-4/3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-9882339	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4+3))^*21$	-10002324	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3^*2-1)$
-9883032	$9-(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3)^*21$	-10002358	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3^*2+1)$
-9883158	$9-(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3)^*21$	-10002596	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-9884574	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4+3))^*-21$	-10002630	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-9894420	$-9*876*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2-1)$	-10003429	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3^*(2+1))$
-9910188	$-9*876*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2+1)$	-10005554	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4+321)$
-9910719	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^*32)+1)$	-10005690	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4+321)$
-9910737	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^*32)-1)$	-10007492	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+432-1)$
-9921933	$-9*((8+76)^*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$	-10007508	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+432)+1$
-9923067	$-9*((8+76)^*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$	-10007509	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+432)^{\wedge}1$
-9930516	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-10007510	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+432)-1$
-9930550	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2)-1)$	-10007526	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+432+1)$
-9947023	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*(3+2)-1)$	-10017556	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-9947057	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*(3+2)+1)$	-10017590	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-9970789	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-10021993	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^*321)$
-9978337	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^*321)$	-10029541	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-9979282	$-9*((8+7^{\wedge}6-6+5+4))^*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-10031241	$9-(8^*7-6)^*5^{\wedge}4^*321$
-9982740	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-10053273	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*(-3-2)+1)$
-9982774	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-10053307	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*(-3-2)-1)$
-9992804	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-432-1)$	-10056384	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(5+4-3)^*21)$
-9992820	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-432)+1$	-10059602	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^*(3+21))$
-9992821	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-432)^{\wedge}1$	-10069780	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5-(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-9992822	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-432)-1$	-10069814	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-9992838	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-432+1)$	-10222848	$9*87*(6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
-9994640	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4-321)$	-10232244	$-9*87*(6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
-9994776	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4-321)$	-10234930	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43^*2+1)$
-9996901	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^*(2+1))$	-10235126	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43^*2+1)$
-9997700	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-10235800	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(43^*2+1)$
-9997734	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-10235996	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(43^*2+1)$
-9998329	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-10237178	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$
-9998448	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^*4)^*(3+2)-1)$	-10239670	$9-(8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}-4+321$
-9998482	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^*4)^*(3+2)+1)$	-10239688	$9-(8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}-4+321$
-9999060	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	-10240312	$9-(8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}-4-321$
-9999094	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$	-10240330	$9-(8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}-4-321$
-9999128	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3+2+1)$	-10249526	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
-9999315	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5+(4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-10259487	$(9-87^*6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32-1)$
-9999349	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5+(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-10260513	$(9-87^*6)^*(5^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$
-9999413	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-43)+21$	-10276353	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^*321)$
-9999455	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-43)-21$	-10278693	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}(3^*2+1))$
-9999642	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-10321506	$9*87*(6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$
-9999756	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5+4^*3^*2)+1$	-10330902	$-9*87*(6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$
-9999758	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5+4^*3^*2)-1$	-10353085	$(9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3))^*(2+1)$
-9999776	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4)+321$	-10353139	$(-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5-4/3))^*(2+1)$
-9999838	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-10398339	$(-9+8^*(7/6-5))^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-9999842	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5+4^*(3+2)-1)$	-10427102	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^*(3-21))$
-9999912	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4)+321$	-10439469	$9-87^*6*(5^{\wedge}4^*32-1)$
-9999978	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5+4^*3-2+1)$	-10439487	$-9-87^*6*(5^{\wedge}4^*32-1)$
-10000352	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^*3-2+1)$	-10440513	$9-87^*6*(5^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$
-10000418	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4)-321$	-10440531	$-9-87^*6*(5^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$
-10000420	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^*3+2+1)$	-10485103	$9+8*(76-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-10000488	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5-4*(3+2)+1)$	-10485121	$-9+8*(76-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-10000492	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-10485135	$9+8*(76-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-10000539	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+43-21)$	-10485183	$9+8*(76-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-10000554	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4)-321$	-10485201	$-9+8*(76-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-10000572	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5-4^*3^*2)+1$	-10485911	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7/6+5)^*(4/3+2)-1$
-10000574	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*-5-4^*3^*2)-1$	-10486319	$9-8*(76+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-10000688	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-10486367	$9-8*(76+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-10000726	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3/2+1)$	-10486399	$9-8*(76+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-10000760	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-10565298	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6^*5/4-321)$
-10000794	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-10573101	$(-9-8*(7/6+5))^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-10000875	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+43)+21$	-10583478	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-10000917	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+43)-21$	-10583622	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-10000947	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*(3+2)+1)$	-10585521	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6^*5/4-321)$
-10000981	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-10586097	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6^*5/4-32)-1)$
-10001015	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+(4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-10586115	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6^*5/4-32)+1)$
-10001202	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	-10587185	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2)+1$
-10001236	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	-10587187	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2)-1$
-10001270	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$	-10587329	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2)+1$
-10001304	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3+2+1)$	-10587331	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2)-1$
-10001848	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^*4)^*(3+2)-1)$	-10587501	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6^*5+43)^*2-1)$
-10001882	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^*4)^*(3+2)+1)$	-10588005	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6^*5/4-3)-21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-10588313	$9^*(8-(7^6*5-4/3)^2)+1$	-11114277	$(9+8)*(7^6*5-4^{\wedge}(3^2-1))$
-10588315	$9^*(8-(7^6*5-4/3)^2)-1$	-11162004	$98^*(-7^6+5^{\wedge}4*3^2+1)$
-10588319	$9^*(8-(7^6*5-4+3)^2)+1$	-11162200	$98^*(-7^6+5^{\wedge}4*3^2-1)$
-10588361	$9^*(8-(7^6*5+4/3)^2)+1$	-11175287	$(9^*8-7^6*5)*(4*(3+2)-1)$
-10588363	$9^*(8-(7^6*5+4/3)^2)-1$	-11176557	$98-7^6*((5+43)^2-1)$
-10588457	$-9^*(8+(7^6*5-4/3)^2)+1$	-11176753	$-98-7^6*((5+43)^2-1)$
-10588459	$-9^*(8+(7^6*5-4/3)^2)-1$	-11178023	$(9^*8+7^6*5)*(-4*(3+2)+1)$
-10588501	$-9^*(8+(7^6*5+4-3)^2)-1$	-11234655	$9+8^*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*321)$
-10588505	$-9^*(8+(7^6*5+4/3)^2)+1$	-11234673	$-9+8^*7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*321)$
-10588507	$-9^*(8+(7^6*5+4/3)^2)-1$	-11235327	$9-8^*7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*321)$
-10588815	$-9^*(8*(7^6*5/4+3)+21)$	-11235345	$-9-8^*7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*321)$
-10589031	$9^*((8-7^6*5-43)^2+1)$	-11235904	$(-9^*(8*(7+6*5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}-2)^{\wedge}-1$
-10589319	$9^*((8+7^6*5+43)^2-2+1)$	-11284602	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1))$
-10589489	$9^*(8-(7^6*5+4^{\wedge}3)^2)+1$	-11289527	$9^*(8-(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2)+1$
-10589491	$9^*(8-(7^6*5+4^{\wedge}3)^2)-1$	-11289529	$9^*(8-(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2)-1$
-10589633	$-9^*(8+(7^6*5+4^{\wedge}3)^2)+1$	-11289671	$-9^*(8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2)+1$
-10589635	$-9^*(8+(7^6*5+4^{\wedge}3)^2)-1$	-11289673	$-9^*(8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2)-1$
-10590705	$-9^*(8+(7^6*5/4+32)-1)$	-11291472	$(98-(7^6-5)^4)*(3+21)$
-10590723	$-9^*(8*(7^6*5/4+32)+1)$	-11292312	$-9^*8*((7^6-5)^4/3-21)$
-10591299	$-9^*(8^*7^6*5/4+321)$	-11292432	$(98-(7^6+5)^4)*(3+21)$
-10593198	$9^*(8-(7^6+54)*(3^2+1))$	-11293623	$9+(8-(7^6-5)^4)*(3+21)$
-10593342	$-9^*(8-(7^6+54)*(3^2+1))$	-11293635	$-9^*(8*(7^6-5)^4/3-21)$
-10611522	$-9^*8*(7^6*5/4+321)$	-11293641	$-9+(8-(7^6-5)^4)*(3+21)$
-10619469	$(-9-87^6)*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	-11293647	$9-8*((7^6-5)^4*3-21)$
-10620531	$(-9-87^6)*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	-11293665	$-9-8*((7^6-5)^4*3-21)$
-10696504	$-98*((7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-11293726	$98-(7^6-5)^4*(3+21)$
-10696700	$-98*((7+6)^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-11293779	$(-9-8*((7^6-5)^4-3))*(2+1)$
-10737566	$9^*(8+7^6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-11293869	$(9-8*((7^6-5)^4+3))*(2+1)$
-10737568	$9^*(8+7^6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-11293922	$-98-(7^6-5)^4*(3+21)$
-10737710	$9^*(-8+7^6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-11293983	$9-8*((7^6-5)^4*3+21)$
-10737712	$9^*(-8+7^6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-11294013	$-9^*(8*(7^6-5)^4/3+21)$
-10768412	$(-9-8)*((7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-11294595	$-9^*(8*(7^6+5)^4/3-21)$
-10768446	$(-9-8)*((7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-11294607	$9-8*((7^6+5)^4*3-21)$
-10807416	$9+(8+7)^6*(5^{\wedge}4-4*32-1)$	-11294686	$98-(7^6+5)^4*(3+21)$
-10829663	$-9^*(8*(7^6-5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-11294739	$(-9-8*((7^6+5)^4-3))*(2+1)$
-10829665	$-9^*(8*(7^6-5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-11294829	$(9-8*((7^6+5)^4+3))*(2+1)$
-10830383	$-9^*(8*(7^6+5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-11294882	$-98-(7^6+5)^4*(3+21)$
-10830385	$-9^*(8*(7^6+5)+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-11294943	$9-8*((7^6+5)^4*3+21)$
-10833246	$9^*(8^*7-6/5^{\wedge}4*321)$	-11294967	$9-(8+(7^6+5)^4)*(3+21)$
-10833615	$9^*(8+7-6^*5^{\wedge}4*321)$	-11294973	$-9^*(8*(7^6+5)^4/3+21)$
-10833759	$-9^*(8-7+6^*5^{\wedge}4*321)$	-11296176	$(98+(7^6-5)^4)*(-3-21)$
-10833885	$-9^*(8+7+6^*5^{\wedge}4*321)$	-11296296	$-9^*8*((7^6+5)^4/3+21)$
-10834254	$-9^*(8^*7+6/5^{\wedge}4*321)$	-11297136	$(98+(7^6+5)^4)*(-3-21)$
-10840443	$9^*(8-7^6*5^{\wedge}43/21)$	-11315227	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$
-10840587	$-9^*(8+7^6*5^{\wedge}43/21)$	-11343794	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*3-21)$
-10917102	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*(3^2+1))$	-11344970	$-98*(7^6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*(2+1))$
-10919454	$(-98+7)^6*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	-11345558	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*3-2-1)$
-10919909	$(-98+7)^6*(6^*5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	-11345754	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*3-2+1)$
-10920546	$(-98+7)^6*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	-11345803	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-10985058	$-9^*((87+6)^6*5^{\wedge}4-3)^2*21$	-11345831	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*3)+21$
-10986192	$-9^*((87+6)^6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^2*21$	-11345873	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*3)-21$
-10989925	$(-9+8/(7+6))^5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-11345901	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-10999697	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)^4*(-4-3/2)+1)$	-11345950	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*3+2-1)$
-10999731	$(9+8)*((7^6-5)^4*(-4-3/2)-1)$	-11346146	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1)$
-11000632	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)^4*(-4-3/2)+1)$	-11346734	$-98*(7^6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)*(2+1))$
-11000666	$(9+8)*((7^6+5)^4*(-4-3/2)-1)$	-11376477	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*(3/2+1))$
-11009698	$98+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-11406416	$-98*(7^6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^2-1)$
-11009733	$98+7^6*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-11406612	$-98*(7^6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^2+1)$
-11009747	$98+7^6*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-11407592	$-98*(7^6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)^2-1)$
-11009782	$98+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-11407788	$-98*(7^6-(5^{\wedge}4-3)^2+1)$
-11009929	$-98+7^6*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-11411855	$98-7^6*((5+43)^2+1)$
-11010018	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7+6^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-11412051	$-98-7^6*((5+43)^2+1)$
-11010042	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7+6^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-11437629	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*3/2-1)$
-11010054	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7+6^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-11498928	$-98*(7^6-(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1)$
-11010078	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7+6^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-11508977	$-98*7^6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1)$
-11010167	$98-7^6*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-11510227	$-98*7^6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1)$
-11010202	$98-7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-11514602	$-98*7^6+5^{\wedge}4*(3+21)$
-11039602	$-98*(7^6-5^{\wedge}4*(3^2-1))$	-11518352	$-98*7^6-5^{\wedge}4*(3-21)$
-11108816	$9^*(8-(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4-3))^{\wedge}-2)+1$	-11519424	$(-9-87)^6*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$
-11108818	$9^*(8-(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4-3))^{\wedge}-2)-1$	-11520576	$(-9-87)^6*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$
-11108960	$-9^*(8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4-3))^{\wedge}-2)+1$	-11540852	$-98*7^6+5^{\wedge}4*(3-21)$
-11108962	$-9^*(8+(7/(6^{\wedge}5+4-3))^{\wedge}-2)-1$	-11544602	$-98*7^6-5^{\wedge}4*(3+21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-11548977	$-98*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(32-1)$	-11801223	$-9*(87*6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-11550227	$-98*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(32+1)$	-11801943	$-9*(8*76+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-11560276	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$	-11801997	$-9*(8*76+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-11566891	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4/3-21)$	-11804319	$-9*(876+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-11568652	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4/3-21)$	-11804355	$-9*(876+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-11568670	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4/3-21)$	-11804363	$-9*(876+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-11621379	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3/2-1)$	-11804365	$-9*(876+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-11621575	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3/2+1)$	-11804373	$-9*(876+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-11647153	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5*4*(3+2)-1)$	-11804409	$-9*(876+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-11651416	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$	-11882451	$98-7^{\wedge}6*((54-3)*2-1)$
-11651612	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$	-11882647	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*((54-3)*2-1)$
-11652592	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$	-11897004	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3*2-1)$
-11652788	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$	-11897200	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3*2+1)$
-11682727	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3/2+1))$	-11916304	$(-9/((8+(7-6^{\wedge}5)*4)/3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-11712470	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*(2+1))$	-11955249	$(-9+8*7)*(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-11713058	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3-2-1)$	-11955343	$(-9+8*7)*(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-11713254	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3-2+1)$	-11979401	$(9-8*76)*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$
-11713303	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-11980599	$(9-8*76)*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$
-11713331	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)+21$	-11998141	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5*4)*3*2-1)$
-11713373	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)-21$	-11998175	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5*4)*3*2+1)$
-11713401	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-11999263	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*3*2-1)$
-11713450	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3+2-1)$	-11999297	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*3*2+1)$
-11713646	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1)$	-11999671	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4*3/2-1)$
-11714234	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)*(2+1))$	-11999705	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4*3/2+1)$
-11715410	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$	-12000113	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*3*2+1)$
-11743977	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	-12000147	$(9+8)*(-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4-3)+2+1)$
-11764810	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5/4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-12000171	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5/4+3))*(2+1)$
-11764990	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5/4)*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-12000225	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5/4+3))*(2+1)$
-11774602	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1))$	-12000249	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(-5-4+3)-2-1)$
-11788551	$9*(876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-12000283	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*3*2-1)$
-11788587	$9*(876-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-12000691	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4*3/2-1)$
-11788595	$9*(876-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12000725	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4*3/2+1)$
-11788597	$9*(876-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12001099	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*3*2-1)$
-11788605	$9*(876-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-12001133	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*3*2+1)$
-11788641	$9*(876-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-12002221	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5*4)*3*2-1)$
-11790963	$9*(8*76-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-12019602	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-11790999	$9*(8*76-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-12044781	$9*(8/76+5)*(-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-11791017	$9*(8*76-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-12063931	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*3*2-1)$
-11791053	$9*(8*76-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-12063965	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*3*2+1)$
-11791737	$9*(8*76-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-12117749	$98-7^{\wedge}6*((54-3)*2+1)$
-11791773	$9*(8*76-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-12117945	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*((54-3)*2+1)$
-11791791	$9*(8*76-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-12142102	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-11791827	$9*(8*76-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-12173112	$-9*((87-6*5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2-1$
-11793455	$9*(8*7*6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12173130	$-9*((87-6*5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2+1$
-11793457	$9*(8*7*6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12234911	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6/5)*(4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
-11795543	$9*(8*(7+6)-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12236081	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6/5)*(4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
-11795545	$9*(8*(7+6)-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12239388	$9*(8-76)*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$
-11795823	$-9*(8-76+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-12240612	$9*(8-76)*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$
-11795859	$-9*(8-76+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-12252205	$-98*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3/2-1)$
-11796173	$-9*(8-7*6+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12252401	$-98*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3/2+1)$
-11796175	$-9*(8-7*6+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12319311	$(-9+8*7)*(6*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-11796407	$9*(8*(7-6)-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12319405	$(-9+8*7)*(6*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-11796409	$9*(8*(7-6)-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12320204	$(-9+8*7)*(6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-11796551	$-9*(8*(7-6)+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12320298	$(-9+8*7)*(6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-11796553	$-9*(8*(7-6)+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12320623	$98-(7*6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-11796785	$9*(8-7*6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12320649	$9*8-(7*6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-11796787	$9*(8-7*6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12320674	$(-9+8*7)*(6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-11797164	$-9*(8*7-6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-12320717	$98-(7*6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-11797191	$-9*(8+76+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-12320743	$9*8-(7*6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-11797200	$9*(-87+6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-12320793	$9*-8-(7*6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-11797218	$9*(-87+6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-12320887	$9*-8-(7*6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-11797227	$-9*(8+76+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-12320913	$-98-(7*6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-11797254	$-9*(87-6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-12322131	$(9-8*7)*(6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-11797272	$-9*(87+6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-12322225	$(9-8*7)*(6*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-11797308	$9*(-87-6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-12339383	$(-9-8*76)*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$
-11797326	$9*(-87-6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-12340617	$(-9-8*76)*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$
-11797362	$-9*(87+6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-12351624	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3)*21$
-11797415	$-9*(8*(7+6)+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12351642	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3)*21$
-11797417	$-9*(8*(7+6)+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12351960	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$
-11799503	$-9*(8*7*6+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-12351978	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$
-11799505	$-9*(8*7*6+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-12352795	$98-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4*3)*21$
-11801169	$-9*(8*7*6+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-12352929	$(9*8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3))*(2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-12352940	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+4/3)*21$	-12711933	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+54)*3/2+1)$
-12352950	$(9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+3))*(2+1)$	-12711996	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+54)*3/2+1)$
-12352991	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4*3)*21$	-12783483	$(9-8^{\wedge}7)*6-5^{\wedge}4*321$
-12352996	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-4/3)*21$	-12783591	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)*6-5^{\wedge}4*321$
-12353004	$(-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+3))*(2+1)$	-12809678	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)*21)$
-12353075	$98-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4/3)*21$	-12822026	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)*21)$
-12353215	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4/3)*21$	-12855248	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-12353276	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4/3)*21$	-12855250	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-12353286	$(9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+3))*(2+1)$	-12855392	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-12353294	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4/3)*21$	-12855394	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6+5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-12353299	$98-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4*3)*21$	-12941205	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43-21)$
-12353332	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4/3)*21$	-12941557	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43-21)$
-12353340	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+3))*(-2-1)$	-12969080	$9*(8^{\wedge}7-(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-12353361	$(9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3))*(-2-1)$	-12969082	$9*(8^{\wedge}7-(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-12353495	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4*3)*21$	-13040235	$(9*8-7)*(6-5^{\wedge}4*321)$
-12354312	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	-13041015	$(-9*8+7)*(6+5^{\wedge}4*321)$
-12354330	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	-13048946	$(-9/(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)*(4+3)+2))^{\wedge}-1$
-12354648	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3)*21$	-13107241	$9+(8+7-65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-12354666	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3)*21$	-13135283	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4/3+21)$
-12358445	$(-9+8/7)*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-13137284	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4/3+21)$
-12382233	$(9-8^{\wedge}7)*6+5^{\wedge}4*321$	-13157133	$(9-8*7)*(6^{\wedge}(5+4*3)+2+1)$
-12382341	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7)*6+5^{\wedge}4*321$	-13183352	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-12438741	$9-(8*7+6)*5^{\wedge}4*321$	-13294239	$98-7^{\wedge}6*((54+3)*2-1)$
-12438759	$-9-(8*7+6)*5^{\wedge}4*321$	-13294395	$(9+8/7)*(6-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-12479022	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4/3+2+1)$	-13294435	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*((54+3)*2-1)$
-12549053	$(9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*4^{\wedge}3)/(2+1)$	-13385272	$(9/(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-12549059	$(-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*4^{\wedge}3)/(2+1)$	-13387958	$9+(8/(7-65^{\wedge}4*3)/2)^{\wedge}-1$
-12564080	$9*(8^{\wedge}7-(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-13411692	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))*(2+1)$
-12564082	$9*(8^{\wedge}7-(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	-13411971	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))*(2+1)$
-12599370	$(-98-7)*6*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	-13412001	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))*(2+1)$
-12599895	$(-98-7)*(6*5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	-13412280	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))*(2+1)$
-12600105	$(-98-7)*(6*5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	-13428352	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$
-12600630	$(-98-7)*6*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	-13490338	$9-(8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*43/(2+1)$
-12603125	$(9+8/(7+6))*-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-13490983	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*43/(2+1)$
-12632102	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4*(3-21))$	-13491001	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*43/(2+1)$
-12638925	$9*(8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*321))$	-13502440	$98*(7*(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-12639069	$9*(-8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*321))$	-13502636	$98*(7*(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-12639681	$9*(8-7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*321))$	-13529537	$98-7^{\wedge}6*((54+3)*2+1)$
-12639825	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*321))$	-13550852	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$
-12686193	$(9-8*7)*(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-13599320	$(-98*7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$
-12686287	$(9-8*7)*(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-13600680	$(-98*7+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$
-12700188	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*3/2-1)$	-13671770	$98-7*((6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-12700251	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3/2-1)$	-13671784	$98-7*((6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-12700269	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3/2+1)$	-13671796	$9*8-7*((6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-12700332	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*3/2+1)$	-13671810	$9*8-7*((6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-12705317	$9*((8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4)*3+2)+1$	-13671940	$-9*8-7*((6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-12705319	$9*((8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4)*3+2)-1$	-13671954	$-9*8-7*((6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-12705353	$9*((8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4)*3-2)+1$	-13679244	$9*(8-76*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1))$
-12705355	$9*((8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4)*3-2)-1$	-13679388	$-9*(8+76*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1))$
-12705435	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4*3-21)$	-13680612	$9*(8-76*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1))$
-12705454	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-13680756	$-9*(8+76*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1))$
-12705650	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-13839308	$(-98*7-6)*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$
-12705896	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*54)*(3-2+1)$	-13840692	$(-98*7-6)*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$
-12705994	$98-7^{\wedge}6*54/(3/2-1)$	-13898304	$-9/8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+43)*21$
-12706003	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4+3)+2)-1$	-13905368	$9*(8-(7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-12706037	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4+3)-2)+1$	-13905370	$9*(8-(7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-12706039	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4+3)-2)-1$	-13905512	$-9*(8+(7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-12706067	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*54)/(3/2-1)$	-13905514	$-9*(8+(7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-12706145	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4+3)-2)+1$	-13961276	$-98*76*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-12706147	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4+3)-2)-1$	-13968724	$-98*76*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-12706181	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4+3)+2)+1$	-13999585	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(-4-3)+2+1)$
-12706190	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*54/(3/2-1)$	-13999619	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4+3)-2+1)$
-12706288	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(-3+2-1)$	-13999653	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4+3)+2-1)$
-12706515	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4*3-21)$	-14000133	$98+7^{\wedge}6*5-4*(32-1)$
-12706534	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-14000809	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+3)-2+1)$
-12706730	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-14000843	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+3)+2-1)$
-12706829	$9*((8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4)*-3+2)+1$	-14000877	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+3)+2+1)$
-12706831	$9*((8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4)*-3+2)-1$	-14116272	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6*5-4)/3-21)$
-12706865	$-9*((8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4)*3+2)+1$	-14116317	$(9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3))*(2+1)$
-12706867	$-9*((8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4)*3+2)-1$	-14116371	$(-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3))*(2+1)$
-12711852	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+54)*3/2-1)$	-14116464	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)/3-21)$
-12711915	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+54)*3/2-1)$	-14116839	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-43)*(2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-14117565	$(9-8*(7^6*5-4^3))^*(2+1)$	-14445936	$-9*8*(7+6+5^4*321)$
-14117595	$-9*(8*(7^6*5-4)/3-21)$	-14456596	$(-9-8)*(7^6*5+4^3^2-1)$
-14117607	$9-8*((7^6*5-4)^3-21)$	-14456630	$(-9-8)*(7^6*5+4^3^2+1)$
-14117619	$(9+8*(7^6*5-4^3))^*(-2-1)$	-14548921	$9*(8-(7/6+5)^4^3^2-1)$
-14117686	$98-(7^6*5-4)^*(3+21)$	-14549063	$-9*(8+(7/6+5)^4^3^2)+1$
-14117739	$(-9-8*(7^6*5-4-3))^*(2+1)$	-14549065	$-9*(8+(7/6+5)^4^3^2)-1$
-14117821	$(9-8*(7^6*5-4/3))^*(2+1)$	-14584818	$(98-(7^6-5)^4)^*(32-1)$
-14117829	$(9-8*(7^6*5-4+3))^*(2+1)$	-14586058	$(98-(7^6+5)^4)^*(32-1)$
-14117931	$(-9-8*(7^6*5+4-3))^*(2+1)$	-14587599	$9+(8-(7^6-5)^4)^*(32-1)$
-14117939	$(-9-8*(7^6*5+4/3))^*(2+1)$	-14587758	$98-(7^6-5)^4*(32-1)$
-14118021	$(9-8*(7^6*5+4+3))^*(2+1)$	-14587954	$-98-(7^6-5)^4*(32-1)$
-14118074	$-98-(7^6*5+4)^*(3+21)$	-14588467	$9+8*7^6*(5-4/3^2+1)$
-14118075	$(-9-8*(7^6*5+4+3))^*(2+1)$	-14588998	$98-(7^6+5)^4*(32-1)$
-14118135	$9-8*((7^6*5+4)^3+21)$	-14589194	$-98-(7^6+5)^4*(32-1)$
-14118141	$(9-8*(7^6*5+4^3))^*(2+1)$	-14589335	$9-(8+(7^6+5)^4)^*(32-1)$
-14118165	$-9*(8*(7^6*5+4)/3+21)$	-14590894	$(98+(7^6-5)^4)^*(-32+1)$
-14118195	$(9+8*(7^6*5+4^3))^*(-2-1)$	-14592134	$(98+(7^6+5)^4)^*(-32+1)$
-14118903	$9-8*(7^6*5+4/3)^*(2+1)$	-14676359	$9+8*7*(65-4^3^2+1)$
-14118921	$-9-8*(7^6*5+4/3)^*(2+1)$	-14676407	$9+8*(7*(65-4^3^2)+1)$
-14119296	$-9*(8*(7^6*5-4)/3+21)$	-14676423	$9+8*(7*(65-4^3^2)-1)$
-14119389	$(9-8*(7^6*5+4^3))^*(2+1)$	-14676425	$-9+8*(7*(65-4^3^2)+1)$
-14119443	$(-9-8*(7^6*5+4/3))^*(2+1)$	-14676441	$-9+8*(7*(65-4^3^2)-1)$
-14119488	$-9*(8*(7^6*5+4)/3+21)$	-14676471	$9+8*7*(65-4^3^2-1)$
-14155001	$9*(8*7+6*(5-4^3^2))+1$	-14683639	$9-8*7*(65+4^3^2-1)$
-14155003	$9*(8*7+6*(5-4^3^2))-1$	-14683687	$9-8*(7*(65+4^3^2)-1)$
-14155209	$9*(8*7-6*(5+4^3^2)-1)$	-14683703	$9-8*(7*(65+4^3^2)+1)$
-14155372	$9*(8*7+6*(5-4^3^2))-1$	-14683751	$9-8*7*(65+4^3^2+1)$
-14155498	$9*(8-7+6*(5-4^3^2))-1$	-14704325	$(9*8-7^6*5)^*(4^3*2+1)$
-14155514	$-9*(8-7-6*(5-4^3^2))+1$	-14705700	$(9+8-7^6*5)^*(4^3*2+1)$
-14155516	$-9*(8-7-6*(5-4^3^2))-1$	-14705925	$9*(8-7^6*5)^*(4/3^2+1)$
-14155541	$9*(8*7-6*(5+4^3^2))+1$	-14706100	$(9-8-7^6*5)^*(4^3*2+1)$
-14155543	$9*(8*7-6*(5+4^3^2))-1$	-14706150	$(-9+8-7^6*5)^*(4^3*2+1)$
-14155640	$-9*(8+7-6*(5-4^3^2))+1$	-14706550	$(9+8+7^6*5)^*(4^3*2-1)$
-14155642	$-9*(8+7-6*(5-4^3^2))-1$	-14707925	$(9*8+7^6*5)^*(4^3*2-1)$
-14155703	$9*(8-(7-6+5)^4^3^2)+1$	-14758848	$-9*876*(5^4*3-2-1)$
-14155705	$9*(8-(7-6+5)^4^3^2)-1$	-14766723	$-9*(876*(5^4*3-2)-1)$
-14155847	$-9*(8+(7-6+5)^4^3^2)+1$	-14766731	$-9*876*(5^4*3-2)+1$
-14155849	$-9*(8+(7-6+5)^4^3^2)-1$	-14766732	$-9*876*(5^4*3-2)^2+1$
-14155912	$9*(8+7-6*(5+4^3^2))-1$	-14766733	$-9*876*(5^4*3-2)-1$
-14156009	$-9*(8*7-6*(5-4^3^2))+1$	-14766741	$-9*(876*(5^4*3-2)+1)$
-14156011	$-9*(8*7-6*(5-4^3^2))-1$	-14774616	$-9*876*(5^4*3-2+1)$
-14156036	$9*(8-7-6*(5+4^3^2))+1$	-14778558	$-9*876*(5^4*3-2^2-1)$
-14156038	$9*(8-7-6*(5+4^3^2))-1$	-14786442	$-9*876*(5^4*3+2^2-1)$
-14156054	$-9*(8-7+6*(5+4^3^2))+1$	-14790384	$-9*876*(5^4*3+2-1)$
-14156056	$-9*(8-7+6*(5+4^3^2))-1$	-14798259	$-9*(876*(5^4*3+2)-1)$
-14156180	$-9*(8+7+6*(5+4^3^2))+1$	-14798267	$-9*876*(5^4*3+2)+1$
-14156182	$-9*(8+7+6*(5+4^3^2))-1$	-14798268	$-9*876*(5^4*3+2)^2+1$
-14156280	$9*(8-87+6*(5-4^3^2)+1)$	-14798269	$-9*876*(5^4*3+2)-1$
-14156298	$9*(8-87+6*(5-4^3^2))-1$	-14798277	$-9*(876*(5^4*3+2)+1)$
-14156343	$-9*(87-6*(5-4^3^2)-1)$	-14806152	$-9*876*(5^4*3+2+1)$
-14156549	$-9*(8*7+6*(5+4^3^2))+1$	-14823135	$9-8*(7^6-5)/4^3*21$
-14156551	$-9*(8*7+6*(5+4^3^2))-1$	-14823597	$9+(8-7^6*(5+4-3))^*21$
-14156775	$-9*(87+6*(5+4^3^2)-1)$	-14823933	$9-(8+7^6*(5+4-3))^*21$
-14156820	$-9*(87+6*(5+4^3^2)-1)$	-14824395	$9-8*(7^6+5)/4^3*21$
-14156838	$-9*(87+6*(5+4^3^2)+1)$	-14825832	$(98+7^6*(5+4-3))^*-21$
-14156883	$-9*(87+6*(5+4^3^2+1))$	-14940860	$9*-8-(7^6-5)^*(4^3*2-1)$
-14159922	$98*(7^6+5-4^3^2+1)$	-14941325	$98+7^6*(5-4*(32+1))$
-14160118	$98*(7^6+5-4^3^2-1)$	-14941521	$-98+7^6*(5-4*(32+1))$
-14160902	$98*(7^6-5-4^3^2+1)$	-14942130	$9*-8-(7^6+5)^*(4^3*2-1)$
-14161098	$98*(7^6-5-4^3^2-1)$	-15013077	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-43^2+1)$
-14220368	$9*(8-(7+6*5^4/3)^2)+1$	-15058956	$(9-(8*7^6-5)^4)^*(3+2-1)$
-14220370	$9*(8-(7+6*5^4/3)^2)-1$	-15059028	$(9+(8*7^6-5)^4)^*(-3-2+1)$
-14220512	$-9*(8+(7+6*5^4/3)^2)+1$	-15059116	$(9-(8/7^6-6+5)^4)^*(3+2-1)$
-14220514	$-9*(8+(7+6*5^4/3)^2)-1$	-15059188	$(9+(8*7^6+5)^4)^*(-3-2+1)$
-14411292	$-98*((7^6-5)/4^3*(3+2)-1)$	-15119244	$-9*(8+76)^*(5^4*32-1)$
-14411488	$-98*((7^6-5)/4^3*(3+2)+1)$	-15120756	$-9*(8+76)^*(5^4*32+1)$
-14412517	$-98*((7^6+5)/4^3*(3+2)-1)$	-15175782	$(98-(7^6-5)^4)^*(2+1)$
-14444064	$9*8*(7+6-5^4*321)$	-15176043	$9+(8-(7^6-5)^4)^*(2+1)$
-14444916	$9*8*(7+6-5^4*321)$	-15176061	$-9+(8-(7^6-5)^4)^*(2+1)$
-14444928	$9*8*(7-6-5^4*321)$	-15176091	$9-(8+(7^6-5)^4)^*(2+1)$
-14445072	$-9*8*(7-6+5^4*321)$	-15176109	$-9-(8+(7^6-5)^4)^*(2+1)$
-14445084	$-9*8*(7+6+5^4*321)$	-15176148	$9*-8-(7^6-5)^*(4^3*2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-15176370	$(98+(7^6-5)*43)*(-2-1)$	-15729828	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+4*(32+1))$
-15176623	$98-7^6*(5+4*(32-1))$	-15729963	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+(4+3)*21)$
-15176819	$-98-7^6*(5+4*(32-1))$	-15731493	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-4+321)$
-15177072	$(98-(7^6+5)*43)*(2+1)$	-15731565	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+4+321)$
-15177333	$9+(8-(7^6+5)*43)*(2+1)$	-15732519	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+432-1)$
-15177381	$9-(8+(7^6+5)*43)*(2+1)$	-15732527	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+432)+1$
-15177438	$9*-8-(7^6+5)*(4^3*2+1)$	-15732529	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+432)-1$
-15177660	$(98+(7^6+5)*43)*(-2-1)$	-15732537	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+432+1)$
-15204196	$98+(7-65)*(4^3^2-1)$	-15736767	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+43*21)$
-15204253	$98+(7-65)*4^3^2+1$	-15740196	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+4*321)$
-15204255	$98+(7-65)*4^3^2-1$	-15740736	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+4^3*21)$
-15204449	$-98+(7-65)*4^3^2+1$	-15745272	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+43^2-1)$
-15204451	$-98+(7-65)*4^3^2-1$	-15745290	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+43^2+1)$
-15204508	$-98+(7-65)*(4^3^2+1)$	-15752863	$98-(7/(6/54))^(3+2-1)$
-15291675	$(-9-8*(7/6+5))*(4^3^2-1)$	-15753059	$-98-(7/(6/54))^(3+2-1)$
-15312491	$9-8*7/6/(5^4(-4-3)/21)$	-15779211	$(-9*87-6)*(5^4*32-1)$
-15371398	$-98*((7^6+5)*4/3-21)$	-15780789	$(-9*87-6)*(5^4*32+1)$
-15373407	$-98*(7^6+5)*4/3-2^4-1)$	-15848901	$(9*8+7)*(6-5^4*321)$
-15375514	$-98*((7^6+5)*4/3+21)$	-15849849	$(-9*8-7)*(6+5^4*321)$
-15388352	$-98*(7^6+5^4*3*21)$	-15879969	$(-98+7^6*5)*(4-32+1)$
-15411780	$9*(87*(6-5-4)^3^2+1)$	-15882102	$9*((8-7^6*5+4)*3+21)$
-15411798	$9*(87*(6-5-4)^3^2-1)$	-15882370	$(98-7^6*54)*(3/2+1)$
-15466487	$9+8^8(7-6+5)*(4-3*21)$	-15882517	$98+7^6*5*(4-32+1)$
-15525774	$(98-(7^6-5)*4)*(32+1)$	-15882586	$9+(8-7^6*54)*(3/2+1)$
-15527094	$(98-(7^6+5)*4)*(32+1)$	-15882626	$9-(8+7^6*54)*(3/2+1)$
-15528735	$9+(8-(7^6-5)*4)*(32+1)$	-15882713	$-98+7^6*5*(4-32+1)$
-15528753	$-9+(8-(7^6-5)*4)*(32+1)$	-15882860	$(98+7^6*54)*(-3/2-1)$
-15528910	$98-(7^6-5)*4*(32+1)$	-15882984	$-9*(8+(7^6*5+4)*3+21)$
-15529025	$-9-8-(7^6-5)*4*(32+1)$	-15883848	$-9*(8+(7^6*5+43)*(2+1))$
-15529106	$-98-(7^6-5)*4*(32+1)$	-15885261	$(98+7^6*5)*(4-32+1)$
-15530230	$98-(7^6+5)*4*(32+1)$	-15924033	$9^8((8+7)/6)*(5-4^3(3^2-1))$
-15530426	$-98-(7^6+5)*4*(32+1)$	-15926463	$9^8((8+7)/6)*(-5-4^3(3^2-1))$
-15530583	$9-(8+(7^6+5)*4)*(32+1)$	-15953629	$(-9-8/7)*(6*(5+4^3^2)-1)$
-15532242	$(98+(7^6-5)*4)*(-32-1)$	-15990773	$-9*8^7+(6+5)*(4^3^2+1)$
-15533562	$(98+(7^6+5)*4)*(-32-1)$	-15990795	$-9*8^7+(6+5)*(4^3^2-1)$
-15539223	$(-9*87+6)*(5^4*32-1)$	-15999465	$(-9-8)*(((7^6-5)*4-3)^2-1)$
-15540777	$(-9*87+6)*(5^4*32+1)$	-15999567	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)*4^3(3/2)-1)$
-15655293	$9*(87*(6-5^4*32)+1)$	-15999601	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)*4^3(3/2)+1)$
-15655311	$9*(87*(6-5^4*32)-1)$	-15999669	$(-9-8)*(((7^6-5)*4+3)^2-1)$
-15664689	$-9*(87*(6+5^4*32)-1)$	-15999703	$(-9-8)*(((7^6-5)*4+3)^2+1)$
-15664707	$-9*(87*(6+5^4*32)+1)$	-16000087	$9-8*(7^6*(5^4-3)-21)$
-15711990	$9*(-8^7/(6/5)+43^2+1)$	-16000105	$-9-8*(7^6*(5^4-3)-21)$
-15712008	$9*(-8^7/(6/5)+43^2-1)$	-16000423	$9-8*(7^6*(5^4-3)+21)$
-15716544	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-4^3*21)$	-16000825	$(-9-8)*(((7^6+5)*4-3)^2-1)$
-15717084	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-4*321)$	-16000859	$(-9-8)*(((7^6+5)*4-3)^2+1)$
-15720513	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-43*21)$	-16000927	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5)*4^3(3/2)-1)$
-15724743	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-432-1)$	-16001063	$(-9-8)*(((7^6+5)*4+3)^2+1)$
-15724751	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-432)+1$	-16025111	$9*(8+7*(6^5-4^3^2))+1$
-15724753	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-432)-1$	-16025113	$9*(8+7*(6^5-4^3^2))-1$
-15724761	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-432+1)$	-16025255	$-9*(8-7*(6^5-4^3^2))+1$
-15725715	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-4-321)$	-16025257	$-9*(8-7*(6^5-4^3^2))-1$
-15725787	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+4-321)$	-16117815	$98-7^6*(5+4*(32+1))$
-15727317	$9*(-8^7/(6/5)+(4+3)*21)$	-16118011	$-98-7^6*(5+4*(32+1))$
-15727452	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-4*(32+1))$	-16134648	$9*(8-7^6*5^4*3/21)$
-15727776	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-4*(3+21))$	-16134792	$-9*(8+7^6*5^4*3/21)$
-15728232	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-43)+21$	-16235553	$9+8*7^6*(5/4^3-21)$
-15728274	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-43)-21$	-16261708	$(-9/((8+7^6*(5^4-3))^2))^2-1$
-15728283	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-4)+321$	-16406110	$98-7^6*(5^4*(3/2)-1)$
-15728351	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-4^3/2)+1$	-16406145	$98-7^6*(6^5*4^3(3/2)-1)$
-15728353	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-4^3/2)-1$	-16406159	$98-7^6*(6^5*4^3(3/2)+1)$
-15728355	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+4)+321$	-16406194	$98-7^6*(5^4*(3/2)+1)$
-15728463	$9*(-8^7/(6/5)-4/3+21)$	-16406306	$-98-7^6*(5^4*(3/2)-1)$
-15728567	$9*(8^7/(6/-5)+4^3(3/2))+1$	-16406341	$-98-7^6*(6^5*4^3(3/2)-1)$
-15728713	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+4^3(3/2))-1$	-16406355	$-98-7^6*(6^5*4^3(3/2)+1)$
-15728841	$9*(-8^7/(6/5)-4/3-21)$	-16444203	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+43^2(2+1))$
-15728925	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)-4)-321$	-16468802	$(98-7^6*5^4*3)*21$
-15728927	$9*(8^7/(6/-5)-4^3/2)+1$	-16470683	$9+(8-7^6*5^4/3)*21$
-15728929	$9*(8^7/(6/-5)-4^3/2)-1$	-16471019	$9-(8+7^6*5^4/3)*21$
-15728997	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+4)-321$	-16472918	$(98+7^6*5^4/3)*-21$
-15729006	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+43)+21$	-16510986	$-9*(8-7*(65-4^3^2+1))$
-15729048	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+43)-21$	-16511040	$-9*(8-7*(65-4^3^2)-1)$
-15729504	$-9*(8^7/(6/5)+4*(3+21))$	-16511112	$-9*(8-7*(65-4^3^2-1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-16513109	$9*(8+7*(6*5-4^3\wedge 2))+1$	-16940475	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3-21)$
-16513111	$9*(8+7*(6*5-4^3\wedge 2))-1$	-16940493	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3-21)$
-16513253	$-9*(8-7*(6*5-4^3\wedge 2))+1$	-16940519	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4*3)*2+1$
-16513255	$-9*(8-7*(6*5-4^3\wedge 2))-1$	-16940521	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4*3)*2-1$
-16514308	$9*(8+7*(6+5-4^3\wedge 2))-1$	-16940655	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4)*(3-21)$
-16514450	$-9*(8-7*(6+5-4^3\wedge 2))+1$	-16940799	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4)*(3-21)$
-16514452	$-9*(8-7*(6+5-4^3\wedge 2))-1$	-16940951	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4*3)*2+1$
-16514478	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-65-4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-16940953	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4*3)*2-1$
-16514496	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-65-4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-16941087	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5*4)*(3-21)$
-16514936	$9*(8+7*(6-5-4^3\wedge 2))+1$	-16941123	$-9*((8*7^{\wedge}6-54/3)*2-1)$
-16514938	$9*(8+7*(6-5-4^3\wedge 2))-1$	-16941162	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))*(2+1)$
-16515053	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*(4+3)-2)+1$	-16941750	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))*(2-1)$
-16515055	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*(4+3)-2)-1$	-16941959	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4*3)*2+1$
-16515089	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*(4+3)+2)+1$	-16941961	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4*3)*2-1$
-16515091	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)*(4+3)+2)-1$	-16942239	$9+(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4)*(3-21)$
-16515143	$-9*(8+7*(6-5)*4^3\wedge 2)+1$	-16942391	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)-4*3)*2+1$
-16515145	$-9*(8+7*(6-5)*4^3\wedge 2)-1$	-16942393	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)-4*3)*2-1$
-16515206	$-9*(8+7*(6-5+4^3\wedge 2))+1$	-16942419	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+54)*(3-21)$
-16515208	$-9*(8+7*(6-5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$	-16942437	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+54)*(3-21)$
-16515648	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+65-4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-16942743	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*(3-21)$
-16515666	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+65-4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-16944039	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)*2-1)$
-16515694	$9*(8-7*(6+5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$	-16944120	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+54/3)*2+1)$
-16515836	$-9*(8+7*(6+5+4^3\wedge 2))+1$	-16944281	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)+3)*2+1$
-16515838	$-9*(8+7*(6+5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$	-16944283	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)+3)*2-1$
-16516889	$9*(8-7*(6*5+4^3\wedge 2))+1$	-16944327	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)*(3-21)$
-16516891	$9*(8-7*(6*5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$	-16944389	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)-3)*2+1$
-16517033	$-9*(8+7*(6*5+4^3\wedge 2))+1$	-16944391	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)-3)*2-1$
-16517035	$-9*(8+7*(6*5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$	-16949223	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(3-21)$
-16519032	$9*(8-7*(65+4^3\wedge 2-1))$	-16951221	$-9*((8*7^{\wedge}6+543)*2-1)$
-16519158	$9*(8-7*(65+4^3\wedge 2+1))$	-16951239	$-9*((8*7^{\wedge}6+543)*2+1)$
-16519176	$-9*(8+7*(65+4^3\wedge 2-1))$	-16952697	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3-21)$
-16519230	$-9*(8+7*(65+4^3\wedge 2-1))$	-16952715	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3-21)$
-16519248	$-9*(8+7*(65+4^3\wedge 2+1))$	-17004887	$9*(8-7*(6^{\wedge}5+4^3\wedge 2))+1$
-16519302	$-9*(8+7*(65+4^3\wedge 2+1))$	-17004889	$9*(8-7*(6^{\wedge}5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$
-16530612	$-9*8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4\wedge(3/2))+1$	-17005031	$-9*(8+7*(6^{\wedge}5+4^3\wedge 2))+1$
-16530624	$-9*8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4\wedge(3/2))-1$	-17005033	$-9*(8+7*(6^{\wedge}5+4^3\wedge 2))-1$
-16676109	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4*3*21)$	-17019576	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+543)*2-1)$
-16706060	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4+3)*21)$	-17019639	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+543)*2-1)$
-16706256	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4+3)*21)$	-17019657	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+543)*2+1)$
-16739163	$-9*(87+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	-17019720	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+543)*2+1)$
-16739694	$9+(8/7-65)*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-17031447	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3-21)$
-16740837	$-9*(87+6)*(5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	-17031465	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*(3-21)$
-16748118	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6/5^{\wedge}4-4*3*21)$	-17038512	$9*87-65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16822994	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-17038609	$98*7-65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16823020	$9*8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-17038642	$9*87-65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-16823190	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-17038739	$98*7-65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-16824424	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-17039190	$98+7-65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16824450	$9*8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-17039197	$98-(7+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16824620	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-17039199	$9+87-65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16851447	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3-21)$	-17039204	$98-7-65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16851465	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3-21)$	-17039223	$9*8-(7+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16863192	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-543)*2-1)$	-17039249	$98-(7+6)*(5*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16863255	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-543)*2-1)$	-17039275	$9*8-(7+6)*(5*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16863273	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-543)*2+1)$	-17039309	$-98/7-65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16863336	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-543)*2+1)$	-17039320	$98+7-65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-16930197	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3-21)$	-17039327	$98-(7+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-16930215	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*(3-21)$	-17039329	$9+87-65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-16931673	$-9*((8*7^{\wedge}6-543)*2-1)$	-17039334	$98-7-65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-16933239	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54-3)*2-1)$	-17039386	$-98+7-65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16933320	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-54-3)*2+1)$	-17039391	$-9-87-65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16933671	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3-21)$	-17039400	$-98-7-65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16933689	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3-21)$	-17039411	$98/7-65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-16933725	$-9*((8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)+3)*2-1)$	-17039497	$9*-8-(7+6)*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-16934535	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-43)*2-1)$	-17039516	$-98+7-65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-16934616	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5-43)*2+1)$	-17039521	$-9-87-65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-16938521	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)+3)*2+1$	-17039530	$-98-7-65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-16938523	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)+3)*2-1$	-17039981	$-98*7-65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16938567	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)*(3-21)$	-17040078	$-9*87-65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-16938629	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)-3)*2+1$	-17040111	$-98*7-65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-16938631	$-9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5*4)-3)*2-1$	-17040208	$-9*87-65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-16940151	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*(3-21)$	-17056263	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4-32-1)$
-16940169	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*(3-21)$	-17058282	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-17058308	$9*8-(7^6-5)*((4^3)^2+1)$	-17904655	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^4)^3-2-1)$
-17058478	$-98-(7^6-5)*((4^3)^2+1)$	-17904689	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^4)^3-2+1)$
-17058864	$9-(8-7^6*5)*(4-32-1)$	-17994840	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5+4)-321)$
-17059328	$9+(8+7^6*5)*(4-32-1)$	-17997220	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^4)^3-2-1)$
-17059732	$98-(7^6+5)*((4^3)^2+1)$	-17997254	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5^4)^3-2+1)$
-17059758	$9*8-(7^6+5)*((4^3)^2+1)$	-17998903	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5-4)^3-2-1)$
-17059928	$-98-(7^6+5)*((4^3)^2+1)$	-17998937	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5-4)^3-2+1)$
-17061947	$(98+7^6*5)*(4-32-1)$	-17999515	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)^3-2-1)$
-17068689	$-9*(8^7-6-5^4*321)$	-17999549	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)^3-2+1)$
-17068797	$-9*(8^7+6-5^4*321)$	-18000127	$(9+8)*(7^6*(-5-4)+3^2+1)$
-17202430	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3/2-1)$	-18000161	$(9+8)*(7^6*(-5-4)+3^2-1)$
-17202626	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3/2+1)$	-18000178	$(9+8)*(7^6*(-5-4)+3^2+1)$
-17218601	$((9^8-7+6)/-5+43)^2+1$	-18000180	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4-3)-21)$
-17218603	$((9^8-7+6)/-5+43)^2-1$	-18000199	$98-7^6*(54-3)^2+1$
-17218773	$((9^8-7+6)/-5-43)^2+1$	-18000206	$9*(8-7^6*(5^4-3)+2)+1$
-17218775	$((9^8-7+6)/-5-43)^2-1$	-18000208	$9*(8-7^6*(5^4-3)+2)-1$
-17265661	$((9^8+7^6)/-5+43)^2+1$	-18000229	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5+4)-3-2+1)$
-17265663	$((9^8+7^6)/-5+43)^2-1$	-18000242	$9*(8-7^6*(5^4-3)-2)+1$
-17265833	$((9^8+7^6)/-5-43)^2+1$	-18000263	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5+4)-3+2-1)$
-17265835	$((9^8+7^6)/-5-43)^2-1$	-18000312	$9-(8+7^6*(54-3))^2+1$
-17286367	$-98*((7^6-54)^3/2-1)$	-18000331	$(9+8)*(7^6*(-5-4)-3+2-1)$
-17286563	$-98*((7^6-54)^3/2+1)$	-18000352	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4-3)-2)-1$
-17291610	$(98-(7^6-5)*(4+3))^2+1$	-18000365	$(9+8)*(7^6*(-5-4)-3-2+1)$
-17293491	$9+(8-(7^6-5)*(4+3))^2+1$	-18000386	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4-3)+2)+1$
-17293509	$-9+(8-(7^6-5)*(4+3))^2+1$	-18000388	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4-3)+2)-1$
-17293827	$9-(8+(7^6-5)*(4+3))^2+1$	-18000395	$-98-7^6*(54-3)^2+1$
-17293845	$-9-(8+(7^6-5)*(4+3))^2+1$	-18000416	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5+4)+3^2+1)$
-17294961	$9+(8-(7^6+5)*(4+3))^2+1$	-18000433	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5+4)+3^2-1)$
-17295297	$9-(8+(7^6+5)*(4+3))^2+1$	-18000467	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5+4)+3^2+1)$
-17297196	$(98+(7^6+5)*(4+3))^2-1$	-18000558	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4-3)+21)$
-17297245	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3/2-1)$	-18000591	$(98+7^6*(54-3))^2-1$
-17301429	$9-(8-7+65)^3*(4^3-2-1)$	-18000756	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5+4)+3^2+1)$
-17301561	$9-(8-7+65)^3*(4^3+2+1)$	-18001045	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5)^3-2-1)$
-17302243	$-98*((7^6+54)^3/2-1)$	-18001079	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5)^3-2+1)$
-17302439	$-98*((7^6+54)^3/2+1)$	-18001657	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5+4)^3-2-1)$
-17338878	$9-(8/7+65)^3*(4^3-2-1)$	-18001691	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5+4)^3-2+1)$
-17386180	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3/2-1)$	-18003195	$-9*(8*(7/(6/54))^3-21)$
-17386376	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3/2+1)$	-18003340	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^4)^3-2-1)$
-17411954	$98-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2-1)$	-18003374	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^4)^3-2+1)$
-17411980	$9*8-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2-1)$	-18003519	$-9*(8*(7/(6/54))^3+2)-1$
-17412150	$-98-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2-1)$	-18003573	$-9*(8*(7/(6/54))^3+21)$
-17563589	$-9*(8^7-6)+5*(4^3+2+1)$	-18005754	$(-9-8)*7^6*(5+4)+321$
-17563599	$-9*(8^7-6)+5*(4^3+2-1)$	-18095905	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^4)^3-2-1)$
-17563697	$-9*(8^7+6)+5*(4^3+2+1)$	-18095939	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5^4)^3-2+1)$
-17563707	$-9*(8^7+6)+5*(4^3+2-1)$	-18117937	$9-8*7^6*(5/4-3+21)$
-17577620	$9*(8^7-(6-5+4)^3+2)+1$	-18162216	$-9*(8^7-6*(5^4+3))^2+1$
-17577622	$9*(8^7-(6-5+4)^3+2)-1$	-18165051	$9*(-8^7+(6^5+4+3))^2+1$
-17577991	$9*(8^7-(6-5+4)^3+2)-1$	-18166185	$9*(-8^7+(6^5+4-3))^2+1$
-17578259	$-9*(8^7+(6-5+4)^3+2)+1$	-18169020	$-9*(8^7-6*(5^4-3))^2+1$
-17578261	$-9*(8^7+(6-5+4)^3+2)-1$	-18235214	$9+(8-7^6*5+4)^3*(32-1)$
-17578628	$-9*(8^7+(6-5+4)^3+2)+1$	-18235373	$98-(7^6*5-4)^3*(32-1)$
-17578630	$-9*(8^7+(6-5+4)^3+2)-1$	-18235462	$9+(8-7^6*5-4)^3*(32-1)$
-17578899	$-9*(8^7+(6-5+4)^3+2-1)$	-18235497	$98-7^6*5*(4^3/2-1)$
-17578917	$-9*(8^7+(6-5+4)^3+2+1)$	-18235523	$9*8-7^6*5*(4^3/2-1)$
-17647252	$98-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2+1)$	-18235569	$-98-(7^6*5-4)^3*(32-1)$
-17647277	$9*(8-7^6*5*(4/3+2))+1$	-18235621	$98-(7^6*5+4)^3*(32-1)$
-17647279	$9*(8-7^6*5*(4/3+2))-1$	-18235667	$9*-8-7^6*5*(4^3/2-1)$
-17647421	$-9*(8+7^6*5*(4/3+2))+1$	-18235693	$-98-7^6*5*(4^3/2-1)$
-17647423	$-9*(8+7^6*5*(4/3+2))-1$	-18235710	$9-(8+7^6*5-4)^3*(32-1)$
-17647448	$-98-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2+1)$	-18235817	$-98-(7^6*5+4)^3*(32-1)$
-17794314	$-9*(8^7-6*(5^4+32+1))$	-18235958	$9-(8+7^6*5+4)^3*(32-1)$
-17794359	$-9*(8^7-6*(5^4+32-1))$	-18353172	$9*(8+7^6*(5-4/3-21))$
-17794377	$-9*(8^7-6*(5^4+32+1))$	-18353316	$9*(-8+7^6*(5-4/3-21))$
-17794422	$-9*(8^7-6*(5^4+32-1))$	-18359046	$(9-8^7)*(-6+5^4+3/2)-1$
-17825375	$9-(8-76)^3*(5-4^3+2+1)$	-18359140	$(9-8^7)*(-6+5^4+3/2)+1$
-17825511	$9-(8-76)^3*(5-4^3+2-1)$	-18359610	$(9-8^7)*6*(5+4^3/3)-1$
-17826055	$9+(8-76)^3*(5+4^3+2-1)$	-18359704	$(9-8^7)*6*(5+4^3/3)+1$
-17826191	$9+(8-76)^3*(5+4^3+2+1)$	-18421023	$9-8*(7^6-(5^4)^3)^2+1$
-17882550	$98-7^6*(5+(4+3)^2+1)$	-18421041	$-9-8*(7^6-(5^4)^3)^2+1$
-17882621	$(-9-8*7^6*(5+4/3))^2*(2+1)$	-18460918	$9*(-8^7+(6+5^4/3)^2)+1$
-17882675	$(-9-8*7^6*(5+4/3))^2*(2+1)$	-18460920	$9*(-8^7+(6+5^4/3)^2)-1$
-17882746	$-98-7^6*(5+(4+3)^2+1)$	-18482337	$-9^8(-8+7+6)^3*(5^4+3)/2-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-18505918	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-18864993	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7+6^*5^{\wedge}4*(3/2+1)$
-18505920	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	-18866838	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7+6^*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2-1)$
-18510002	$9+(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4/3-21)$	-18866898	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7+6^*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2+1)$
-18510887	$9+8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4/3-21)$	-18866910	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7+6^*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2-1)$
-18518859	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^*21)$	-18870509	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*2)+1$
-18519939	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+6+5^{\wedge}4*3^*21)$	-18870725	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^*2)+1$
-18520047	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7-6+5^{\wedge}4*3^*21)$	-18870727	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^*2)-1$
-18521127	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^*21)$	-18871814	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6)+5^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1)$
-18559794	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7+6/5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-18871922	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6)+5^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1)$
-18673689	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6)+5^{\wedge}4*321$	-18872736	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}4/3+21)$
-18673737	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7+6+5^{\wedge}4*321$	-18876000	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}4/3+21)$
-18673749	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7-6+5^{\wedge}4*321$	-18876814	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6)-5^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1)$
-18673797	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6)+5^{\wedge}4*321$	-18876922	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6)-5^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1)$
-18683798	$(9-8^{\wedge}7)*6/((5/4-3)^{\wedge}2-2-1)$	-18878009	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^*2)+1$
-18688689	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$	-18878011	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^*2)-1$
-18688797	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7-6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$	-18878227	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*2)-1$
-18689375	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4-3/21)$	-18881826	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7-6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2-1)$
-18694305	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6-5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	-18881838	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7-6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2+1)$
-18694323	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6-5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	-18881898	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7-6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2-1)$
-18694413	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	-18883743	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7-6*5^{\wedge}4*(3/2+1)$
-18694431	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	-18884484	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4/3-21))$
-18699939	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$	-18885807	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*5^{\wedge}4/3+21)$
-18700047	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7-6+5^{\wedge}4*(32-1))$	-18886752	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4/3+21))$
-18706093	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(54^*3-2-1)$	-18887493	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7-6*5^{\wedge}4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-18706289	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(54^*3-2-1)$	-18889487	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-18739314	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+6+5^{\wedge}4*(3+21))$	-18889489	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-18739422	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7-6+5^{\wedge}4*(3+21))$	-18891161	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)+1$
-18755622	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$	-18891163	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)-1$
-18755730	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7-6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$	-18891323	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2)+1$
-18756756	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$	-18891325	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2)-1$
-18756864	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7-6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$	-18896862	$-9/8^{\wedge}-7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^*2-1)$
-18771984	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21))$	-18896874	$-9/8^{\wedge}-7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^*2+1)$
-18772929	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*5^{\wedge}4*3-21)$	-18901719	$-9^*(8*(76^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-18773009	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2)+1)$	-18901737	$-9^*(8*(76^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-18773011	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2))-1$	-18907119	$-9^*(8*(7^*65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-18773225	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2)+1)$	-18908009	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^*2)+1$
-18773227	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2))-1$	-18908011	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^*2)-1$
-18773307	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$	-18908225	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^*2)+1$
-18806543	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)+1$	-18908227	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^*2)-1$
-18806545	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)-1$	-18912609	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21)$
-18806813	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)+1$	-18914877	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21)$
-18806815	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)-1$	-18929376	$-9^*8^*(765+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-18806921	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)+1$	-18929439	$-9^*(8*(765+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-18806923	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)-1$	-18929457	$-9^*(8*(765+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-18807191	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)+1$	-18929520	$-9^*8^*(765+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-18807193	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)-1$	-18941391	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(54^*3-2+1)$
-18819216	$9^*8^*(765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-18941543	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)+1$
-18819279	$9^*(8*(765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-18941545	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)-1$
-18819297	$9^*(8*(765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-18941587	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(54^*3-2+1)$
-18819360	$9^*8^*(765-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-18941813	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)+1$
-18823512	$(9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4)^*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-18941815	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6*5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2)-1$
-18824168	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4)^*(-3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-18941921	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)+1$
-18833859	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21)$	-18941923	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6*5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)-1$
-18836127	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21)$	-18942191	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)+1$
-18840509	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^*2)+1$	-18942193	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)-1$
-18840511	$9^*(-8^{\wedge}7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^*2)-1$	-18957816	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*(3-21))$
-18840725	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^*2)+1$	-18957960	$9^*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*(3-21))$
-18840727	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^*2)-1$	-18958287	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3/21)$
-18841599	$9^*(8*(7^*65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-18975429	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*5^{\wedge}4*3-21)$
-18846999	$9^*(8*(76^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-18975509	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2))+1$
-18851862	$-9/8^{\wedge}-7+6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^*2+1)$	-18975511	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2))-1$
-18851874	$-9/8^{\wedge}-7+6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^*2-1)$	-18975725	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)+1$
-18857411	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2)+1$	-18975727	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2)-1$
-18857413	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2)-1$	-18975807	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$
-18857573	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)+1$	-18976752	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21))$
-18857575	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)-1$	-18983646	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2+1)$
-18859247	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-18984132	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)+2-1)$
-18859249	$9^*8^*(7^*6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-18984618	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2+1)$
-18861243	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7+6*5^{\wedge}4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-18985104	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)^*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3)-2-1)$
-18861984	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4/3+21))$	-18991872	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
-18862929	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3-21)$	-18991980	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$
-18864252	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4/3-21))$	-18993006	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7-6+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-18993114	$-9*(8^7+6+(5^4+3)*21)$	-19579716	$-9*(8^7+6*(5^4-3)*21)$
-19009314	$-9*(8^7-6+5^4*(3+21))$	-19582551	$-9*(8^7+(6*5^4-3)*21)$
-19009422	$-9*(8^7+6+5^4*(3+21))$	-19583685	$-9*(8^7+(6*5^4+3)*21)$
-19048689	$-9*(8^7-6+5^4*(32-1))$	-19586520	$-9*(8^7+6*(5^4+3)*21)$
-19048797	$-9*(8^7+6+5^4*(32-1))$	-19597023	$9-(8*7^6-(5^4)^3)*21$
-19050318	$9*(8+(7^6-54)*(3-21))$	-19597041	$-9-(8*7^6-(5^4)^3)*21$
-19050462	$9*(-8+(7^6-54)*(3-21))$	-19659519	$9-8*(7^6-5^4-3)*21$
-19054323	$9*(-8^7+6-5^4*32-1)$	-19659537	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4-3)*21$
-19054413	$9*(-8^7-6-5^4*32+1)$	-19659960	$9-(8*(7^6-5^4)-3)*21$
-19054431	$9*(-8^7-6-5^4*32-1)$	-19659978	$-9-(8*(7^6-5^4)-3)*21$
-19055826	$9*(8+(7^6-5^4)*(3-21))$	-19660086	$9-(8*(7^6-5^4)+3)*21$
-19055970	$9*(-8+(7^6-5^4)*(3-21))$	-19660104	$-9-(8*(7^6-5^4)+3)*21$
-19057374	$(-98+7^6*(5+4))*(3-21)$	-19660527	$9-8*(7^6-5^4+3)*21$
-19057608	$9*(8+(7^6-5-4)*(3-21))$	-19660545	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4+3)*21$
-19057752	$9*(-8+(7^6-5-4)*(3-21))$	-19711263	$9-8*(7^6-5^4+3)*21$
-19058877	$9*(8-7^6*54/3+21)$	-19725648	$9-(8*7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-19059011	$9*(8-(7^6*(5+4)-3)*2)+1$	-19725666	$-9-(8*7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-19059013	$9*(8-(7^6*(5+4)-3)*2)-1$	-19728903	$9-8*(7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-19059263	$-9*(8+(7^6*(5+4)+3)*2)+1$	-19728921	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-19059265	$-9*(8+(7^6*(5+4)+3)*2)-1$	-19730023	$9-8*(7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-19059372	$9*(-8+(7^6+5-4)*(3-21))$	-19730041	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-19059399	$-9*(8+7^6*54/3+21)$	-19735441	$(9-8*7)*((6^5/4/3)^2-1)$
-19060047	$-9*(8^7+6+5^4*(32+1))$	-19735535	$(9-8*7)*((6^5/4/3)^2+1)$
-19060668	$9*(-8+(7^6+5+4)*(3-21))$	-19737807	$9-8*(7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-19060902	$(98+7^6*(5+4))*(3-21)$	-19737825	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-19062306	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*(3-21))$	-19753431	$9-8*(7^6-5-4^3)*21$
-19062450	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)*(3-21))$	-19753449	$-9-8*(7^6-5-4^3)*21$
-19067814	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*(3-21))$	-19755111	$9-8*(7^6+5-4^3)*21$
-19067958	$9*(-8+(7^6+5^4)*(3-21))$	-19755129	$-9-8*(7^6+5-4^3)*21$
-19074939	$-9*(8^7-6)-5^4*321$	-19755447	$9-8*(7^6-5^4-3)*21$
-19074987	$-9*8^7+6-5^4*321$	-19755465	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4-3)*21$
-19074999	$-9*8^7-6-5^4*321$	-19755888	$9-(8*(7^6-5^4)-3)*21$
-19075047	$-9*(8^7+6)-5^4*321$	-19755906	$-9-(8*(7^6-5^4)-3)*21$
-19092743	$9+8*7^6*(5/(4+3)-21)$	-19756014	$9-(8*(7^6-5^4)+3)*21$
-19092761	$-9+8*7^6*(5/(4+3)-21)$	-19756032	$-9-(8*(7^6-5^4)+3)*21$
-19160316	$9*(8+(7^6+5^4)*(3-21))$	-19756455	$9-8*(7^6-5^4+3)*21$
-19176689	$98-7^6*(5^4*3+2-1)$	-19756473	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4+3)*21$
-19176885	$-98-7^6*(5^4*3+2-1)$	-19756959	$9-8*(7^6-5-4^3)*21$
-19188942	$-9*8^7-6/5*(4^3+2+1)$	-19756977	$-9-8*(7^6-5-4^3)*21$
-19214076	$-98*((7^6*5+4)/3-21)$	-19758303	$9-(8*7^6-5^4+3)*21$
-19216085	$-98*((7^6*5+4)/3-2^2-1)$	-19758321	$-9-(8*7^6-5^4+3)*21$
-19216183	$-98*((7^6*5+4)/3+2^2-1)$	-19758639	$9-8*(7^6+5-4^3)*21$
-19217408	$-98*(7^6*5+4)/(2+1)$	-19758657	$-9-8*(7^6+5-4^3)*21$
-19218192	$-98*((7^6*5+4)/3+21)$	-19759143	$9-8*(7^6-5*(4+3))*21$
-19227609	$9*(-8^7+(6-5^4*3)*21)$	-19760487	$9-8*(7^6-(5+4)^3)*21$
-19228689	$-9*(8^7-6+5^4*3*21)$	-19760508	$9-(8*7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-19228797	$-9*(8^7+6+5^4*3*21)$	-19760526	$-9-(8*7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-19229877	$-9*(8^7+(6+5^4*3)*21)$	-19760648	$9-(8*7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-19242816	$-9*(8^7+(6-5^4/3)^2)+1$	-19760666	$-9-(8*7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-19242818	$-9*(8^7+(6-5^4/3)^2)-1$	-19761159	$9-8*(7^6-5^4-3)*21$
-19287816	$-9*(8^7+(6+5^4/3)^2)+1$	-19761600	$9-(8*(7^6-5^4)-3)*21$
-19287818	$-9*(8^7+(6+5^4/3)^2)-1$	-19761621	$9-(8*7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-19293607	$9-8*(7^6-5)*(43/2-1)$	-19761639	$-9-(8*7^6-5^4*3)*21$
-19293625	$-9-8*(7^6-5)*(43/2-1)$	-19761726	$9-(8*(7^6-5^4)+3)*21$
-19295247	$9-8*(7^6+5)*(43/2-1)$	-19761999	$9-8*(7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-19295265	$-9-8*(7^6+5)*(43/2-1)$	-19762017	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-19411680	$9+(8-7^6*5+4)*(32+1)$	-19762167	$9-8*(7^6-5^4+3)*21$
-19411855	$98-(7^6*5-4)*(32+1)$	-19762839	$9-(8*(7^6-5)-4^3)*21$
-19411944	$9+(8-7^6*5-4)*(32+1)$	-19762857	$-9-(8*(7^6-5)-4^3)*21$
-19411987	$98-7^6*(5^4*3+2+1)$	-19763007	$9-8*(7^6-5-4-3)*21$
-19412051	$-98-(7^6*5-4)*(32+1)$	-19763025	$-9-8*(7^6-5-4-3)*21$
-19412119	$98-(7^6*5+4)*(32+1)$	-19763280	$9-(8*(7^6-5)-4^3)*21$
-19412183	$-98-7^6*(5^4*3+2+1)$	-19763298	$-9-(8*(7^6-5)-4^3)*21$
-19412208	$9-(8+7^6*5-4)*(32+1)$	-19763448	$9-(8*(7^6-5-4)-3)*21$
-19412234	$-9-8-(7^6*5+4)*(32+1)$	-19763847	$9-8*(7^6+5-4^3)*21$
-19412315	$-98-(7^6*5+4)*(32+1)$	-19763903	$9-8*(7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-19412472	$9-(8+7^6*5+4)*(32+1)$	-19763931	$9-(8*(7^6-5)-4^3)*21$
-19412490	$-9-(8+7^6*5+4)*(32+1)$	-19763959	$9-8*(7^6-5-4/3)*21$
-19450023	$9-8*(7^6-5^4*3)*21$	-19764036	$9-(8*(7^6-5)-4-3)*21$
-19450041	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4*3)*21$	-19764155	$9-(8*(7^6-5)-4/3)*21$
-19473471	$9-8/7*65*(4^3+2-1)$	-19764162	$9-(8*(7^6-5)-4+3)*21$
-19496111	$9-8*7^6*5*(4+3/21)$	-19764165	$(9-8*(7^6-5)*(4+3))*(2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-19764173	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)-4/3)^*21$	-19768446	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)+3)^*21$
-19764204	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4-3)^*21$	-19768887	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$
-19764211	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4/3)^*21$	-19769398	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$
-19764219	$(-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$	-19769416	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$
-19764288	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6-5^*(4+3))^*21$	-19769538	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*21$
-19764309	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4-3)^*21$	-19769559	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+(5+4)^3)^*21$
-19764330	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4+3)^*21$	-19770903	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^*(4+3))^*21$
-19764348	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4+3)^*21$	-19771407	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^3)^*21$
-19764351	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4-3)^*21$	-19771425	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^3)^*21$
-19764393	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4^3)^*21$	-19771743	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^3)^*21$
-19764407	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4/3)^*21$	-19773087	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^3)^*21$
-19764425	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4/3)^*21$	-19773105	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^3)^*21$
-19764435	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4^3)^*21$	-19773591	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^3)^*21$
-19764456	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^3)^*21$	-19773609	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^3)^*21$
-19764645	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6-54/3)^*21$	-19774032	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54)-3)^*21$
-19764663	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6-54/3)^*21$	-19774050	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54)-3)^*21$
-19764687	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4-3)^*21$	-19774158	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54)+3)^*21$
-19764729	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4-3)^*21$	-19774176	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54)+3)^*21$
-19764747	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4-3)^*21$	-19774599	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54+3)^*21$
-19764750	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4)-3)^*21$	-19774617	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54+3)^*21$
-19764792	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)-3)^*21$	-19774935	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^3)^*21$
-19764876	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+5-4^3)^*21$	-19774953	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^3)^*21$
-19764900	$(9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$	-19776615	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^3)^*21$
-19764903	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5/(4+3))^*21$	-19776633	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^3)^*21$
-19764953	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4/3)^*21$	-19792239	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^3)^*21$
-19764954	$(9+(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3))^*(-2-1)$	-19792257	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^3)^*21$
-19764967	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-(5-4)/3)^*21$	-19800023	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$
-19765016	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6-(5-4)/3)^*21$	-19800041	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$
-19765079	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+(5-4)/3)^*21$	-19801143	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^3)^*21$
-19765093	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4/3)^*21$	-19801161	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^3)^*21$
-19765100	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+5-4/3)^*21$	-19804398	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^3)^*21$
-19765110	$(9 \cdot (8/7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$	-19804416	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^3)^*21$
-19765143	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5/(4+3))^*21$	-19810278	$(-9 \cdot 8/7)^*((6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-19765156	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+5+4/3)^*21$	-19818783	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^3)^*21$
-19765161	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5/(4+3))^*21$	-19818801	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^3)^*21$
-19765163	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$	-19869519	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$
-19765164	$(9+(8/7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3))^*(-2-1)$	-19869537	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$
-19765254	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)+3)^*21$	-19869960	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)-3)^*21$
-19765296	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)+3)^*21$	-19869978	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)-3)^*21$
-19765314	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)+3)^*21$	-19870086	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)+3)^*21$
-19765317	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5/4+3)^*21$	-19870104	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)+3)^*21$
-19765359	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4+3)^*21$	-19870527	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$
-19765401	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+54/3)^*21$	-19870545	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21$
-19765419	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+54/3)^*21$	-19923011	$9 \cdot (87-6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-19765611	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)-4^3)^*21$	-19933023	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)^*21$
-19765639	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4/3)^*21$	-19954314	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3-1))$
-19765653	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4^3)^*21$	-19954359	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3-1))$
-19765695	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4+3)^*21$	-19954377	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3+1))$
-19765716	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)-4-3)^*21$	-19954422	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7+6^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3+1))$
-19765737	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4+3)^*21$	-19984203	$9^{\wedge}8^*7+65^{\wedge}4^*(3-21)$
-19765835	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)-4/3)^*21$	-19998137	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2-1)$
-19765842	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)-4+3)^*21$	-19998171	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5-4^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$
-19765845	$(9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$	-19999463	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3^*2)-1)$
-19765884	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4-3)^*21$	-19999497	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3^*2)+1)$
-19765891	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4/3)^*21$	-19999939	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*-5+4^3)^*2-1)$
-19765899	$(-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3))^*(2+1)$	-20000075	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5-4-3)^*2-1)$
-19766010	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4+3)^*21$	-20000109	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5-4-3)^*2+1)$
-19766087	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4/3)^*21$	-20000313	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(-5-4-3+2)+1)$
-19766115	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4^3)^*21$	-20000347	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4-3)^*2+1)$
-19766143	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$	-20000551	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4+3)^*2-1)$
-19766199	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4^3)^*21$	-20000585	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4+3)^*2+1)$
-19766598	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)+3)^*21$	-20000721	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^3)^*-2+1)$
-19766766	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4)^3)^*21$	-20000755	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^3)^*-2-1)$
-19766784	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4)^3)^*21$	-20001163	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3^*2)-1)$
-19767039	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4+3)^*21$	-20001197	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3^*2)+1)$
-19767207	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4^{\wedge}3)^*21$	-20002489	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3)^*2-1)$
-19767225	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4^{\wedge}3)^*21$	-20002523	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$
-19767879	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$	-20078653	$(9 \cdot (8/7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^{\wedge}3)/(2+1)$
-19768047	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)^*21$	-20078659	$(9+(8/7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^{\wedge}3)/(-2-1)$
-19768065	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)^*21$	-20079613	$(9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/(2+1)$
-19768320	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)-3)^*21$	-20079619	$(-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)/(2+1)$
-19768425	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+54^3)^*21$	-20080023	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4^3)^*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-20080041	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	-20723589	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)*21)$
-20117685	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*(2+1)$	-20723733	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)*21)$
-20117881	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)*(2+1)$	-20822916	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4/3-21))$
-20117934	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))/2+1)$	-20823060	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4/3-21))$
-20117946	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*(2+1)$	-20823775	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)^*(2+1)$
-20117952	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))/2-1)$	-20823971	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)^*(2+1)$
-20117964	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*(2+1)$	-20824686	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4/3-21))$
-20117994	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*(2+1)$	-20824830	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4/3-21))$
-20118012	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*(2+1)$	-20954335	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(543+2-1)$
-20118077	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)*(2+1)$	-20983440	$(-9-8)*((7/(6^{\wedge}5+4-3))^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-20118273	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*(-2-1)$	-20983474	$(-9-8)*((7/(6^{\wedge}5+4-3))^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-20154869	$9*(8*(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))+2)+1$	-21000618	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6/5^{\wedge}-4^*3*21)$
-20154871	$9*(8*(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))+2)-1$	-21019834	$9-(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4/3+21)$
-20154905	$9*(8*(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))-2)+1$	-21020839	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4/3+21)$
-20154907	$9*(8*(7-6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))-2)-1$	-21025485	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4-3/21))$
-20155877	$-9*(8*(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))-2)+1$	-21025629	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4-3/21))$
-20155879	$-9*(8*(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))-2)-1$	-21059073	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4+32)-1)$
-20155915	$-9*(8*(7+6^{\wedge}(-5+4^*3))+2)-1$	-21059269	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5*(4+32)-1)$
-20184913	$98-7*(6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-21092913	$9*(87-6*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1))$
-20184983	$98-7*((6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-21092958	$9*(87-6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-20184997	$98-7*((6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-21094479	$-9*(87+6*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1))$
-20185009	$98-7*(6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-21094524	$-9*(87+6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-20185023	$9*8-7*((6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-21094542	$-9*(87+6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-20185029	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-21094587	$-9*(87+6*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1))$
-20185039	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-21109023	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)*21$
-20185067	$98-7*(6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-21109041	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)*21$
-20185137	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-21173643	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4+321)$
-20185147	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-21173859	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4+321)$
-20185153	$-9*8-7*((6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-21174003	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4-321)$
-20185167	$-9*8-7*((6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-21174219	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4-321)$
-20234751	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43/2-1)$	-21175263	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-43)/2-1)$
-20234767	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43/2+1)$	-21176235	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4+32+1)$
-20234769	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43/2-1)$	-21176253	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4+32-1)$
-20234785	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43/2+1)$	-21176427	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)+321$
-20236471	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43/2-1)$	-21176477	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4+3^*2)+1$
-20236487	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43/2+1)$	-21176479	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4+3^*2)-1$
-20236489	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43/2-1)$	-21176571	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)+321$
-20253786	$9^{\wedge}8*(7^*6/54)^{\wedge}3+21$	-21176585	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4-3^*2)+1$
-20253828	$9^{\wedge}8*(7^*6/54)^{\wedge}3-21$	-21176587	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4-3^*2)-1$
-20267207	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-21176695	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4+3^*2)-1$
-20267209	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-21176769	$(9+8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3)^*(2+1)$
-20282122	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-21176801	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4-3^*2)+1$
-20282190	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-21176839	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4-3^*2)-1$
-20282224	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-21176871	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3)^*(-2-1)$
-20282292	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-21176945	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4+3^*2)+1$
-20355678	$98*(7^*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-21177053	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4-3^*2)+1$
-20355874	$98*(7^*6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-21177055	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4+3^*2)-1$
-20420433	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-3/21))$	-21177069	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)-321$
-20420577	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-3/21))$	-21177161	$-9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4+3^*2)+1$
-20437303	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5/(4+3)+21)$	-21177163	$-9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4+3^*2)-1$
-20437321	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5/(4+3)+21)$	-21177213	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)-321$
-20442084	$(-9+87)*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-21178377	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+43)/2+1)$
-20442240	$(-9+87)*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-21179421	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4-321)$
-20447196	$-9*8^{\wedge}7+6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-21179637	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4-321)$
-20447208	$-9*8^{\wedge}7+6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-21179781	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4+321)$
-20447256	$-9*8^{\wedge}7-6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-21179997	$-9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*4+321)$
-20447268	$-9*8^{\wedge}7-6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-21189633	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(543+2+1)$
-20452224	$(9-87)*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-21218112	$-9*8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-20452380	$(9-87)*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-21218124	$-9*8^{\wedge}7-6*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-20470998	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43/(2+1)))$	-21233070	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-20479982	$(9-(8^{\wedge}(7/-6)/5)^{\wedge}-4)/(3/2-1)$	-21233088	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7-65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-20480018	$(-9-(8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}-4)/(3/2-1)$	-21233169	$9+(87-6)*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-20588477	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+32-1)$	-21233331	$9+(87-6)*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-20588673	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+32-1)$	-21233979	$9-(87-6)*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-20679939	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7+6-5^{\wedge}4^*321)$	-21234141	$9-(87-6)*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-20680047	$9*(-8^{\wedge}7-6-5^{\wedge}4^*321)$	-21234159	$-9-(87-6)*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-20705335	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43-21)$	-21234240	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-20707095	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43-21)$	-21234258	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-20709288	$9-(8+76-5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-21294445	$(9*8-7^{\wedge}6*543)/(2+1)$
-20709446	$9-(8+76-5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-21294493	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*543)/(-2-1)$
-20709464	$-9-(8+76-5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-21324783	$(-9-8)*((7/(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-20719037	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(543-2+1)$	-21324817	$(-9-8)*((7/(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}-2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-21328011	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3/21))$	-22230630	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-(5+4)^*3)^*21)$
-21328155	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3/21))$	-22231386	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^*4-3)^*21)$
-21412109	$9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5/4-3-21)$	-22232187	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54/3)^*21)$
-21454470	$9^{\wedge}8*(7/6*(5+4)^{\wedge}-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-22232331	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54/3)^*21)$
-21479274	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5/(4+3)-21))$	-22232520	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^*4+3)^*21)$
-21479418	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5/(4+3)-21))$	-22233321	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5-4-3)^*21)$
-21491106	$98^*((-7^{\wedge}6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^*2+1)$	-22233465	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4-3)^*21)$
-21491302	$98^*((-7^{\wedge}6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^*2-1)$	-22234410	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4^*3)^*21)$
-21502584	$9^{\wedge}8*(76/54^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-22234473	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^*4/3)^*21)$
-21592251	$9^{\wedge}8*(7/6/(-5-4)^{\wedge}3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-22234536	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4/3)^*21)$
-21627210	$-9^*(8+7/6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-22234599	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4+3)^*21)$
-21647239	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3)-21)$	-22234896	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5+4/3)^*21)$
-21647413	$(9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3))/(2+1)$	-22234977	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4-3)^*21)$
-21647419	$(-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3))/(2+1)$	-22235040	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4/3)^*21)$
-21647575	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3)+21)$	-22235318	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-21705246	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43/2-1))$	-22235355	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4-3)^*21)$
-21705390	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43/2-1))$	-22235421	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)^*21$
-21707091	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(43/2-1))$	-22235500	$98-(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)^*21$
-21707235	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(43/2-1))$	-22235547	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)^*21$
-21757941	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7-(6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-22235624	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-21757963	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7-(6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-22235626	$98-(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)^*21$
-21764768	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4+3^{\wedge}-2)+1$	-22235642	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-21764770	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4+3^{\wedge}-2)-1$	-22235680	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-21764967	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3+2+1)$	-22235696	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)^*21$
-21765163	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3+2+1)$	-22235698	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-21881214	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)^*21)$	-22235741	$-9-8-(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)^*21$
-21881358	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)^*21)$	-22235757	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)^*21$
-21933207	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3/21))$	-22235822	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)^*21$
-21977343	$-9/(8*(7+6-5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}-2+1$	-22235883	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)^*21$
-21977345	$-9/(8*(7+6-5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}-2-1$	-22235901	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)^*21$
-22000265	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3*(2+1))$	-22236004	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-22000291	$9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3*(2+1))$	-22236111	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4+3)^*21)$
-22000435	$-9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3*(2+1))$	-22236426	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4/3)^*21)$
-22000461	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3*(2+1))$	-22236489	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4+3)^*21)$
-22019583	$9+(8+76)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-22236867	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4-3)^*21)$
-22019751	$9+(8+76)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-22236930	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4/3)^*21)$
-22020423	$9-(8+76)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-22236993	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^*4/3)^*21)$
-22020502	$-98/(7/(6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1))$	-22237056	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4^*3)^*21)$
-22020530	$-98/(7/(6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1))$	-22238001	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4+3)^*21)$
-22020591	$9-(8+76)^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-22238946	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^*4-3)^*21)$
-22041069	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3-21)$	-22238991	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)^*21)$
-22041087	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3-21)$	-22239135	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54/3)^*21)$
-22057938	$(98+7^{\wedge}6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/-3+21)$	-22240080	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^*4+3)^*21)$
-22116897	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$	-22240836	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+(5+4)^*3)^*21)$
-22117041	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21)$	-22242204	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5*(4+3))^*21)$
-22118031	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$	-22242348	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5*(4+3))^*21)$
-22118175	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4+3)^*21)$	-22242771	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5+4+3)^*21)$
-22129920	$9+87*(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-22242915	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4+3)^*21)$
-22129938	$-9+87*(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-22244661	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5+4+3)^*21)$
-22130094	$9+87*(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-22244805	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4+3)^*21)$
-22130112	$-9+87*(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-22245228	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+54-3)^*21)$
-22175109	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^*4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$	-22245372	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54-3)^*21)$
-22175253	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^*4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$	-22246362	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+54+3)^*21)$
-22194954	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^*4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$	-22246506	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54+3)^*21)$
-22195098	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^*4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$	-22246740	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$
-22196214	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21)$	-22246884	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$
-22196358	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21)$	-22248630	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$
-22205115	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54^*3)^*21)$	-22248774	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$
-22222548	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$	-22266207	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+54^*3)^*21)$
-22222692	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$	-22266351	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54^*3)^*21)$
-22224438	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$	-22274964	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21)$
-22224582	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$	-22275108	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4/3)^*21)$
-22224816	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54-3)^*21)$	-22276224	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5^*4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$
-22224960	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54-3)^*21)$	-22276368	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^*4^{\wedge}3)^*21)$
-22225950	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54+3)^*21)$	-22281441	$(9+8)^*(7^*6-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-22226094	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54+3)^*21)$	-22281509	$(9+8)^*(7^*6-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-22226517	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5-43)^*21)$	-22281543	$(9+8)^*(7^*6-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-22226661	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5-43)^*21)$	-22281611	$(9+8)^*(7^*6-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-22228407	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5-43)^*21)$	-22282869	$(-9-8)^*(7^*6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-22228551	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5-43)^*21)$	-22282937	$(-9-8)^*(7^*6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-22228974	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5*(4+3))^*21)$	-22282971	$(-9-8)^*(7^*6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-22229118	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5*(4+3))^*21)$	-22283039	$(-9-8)^*(7^*6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-22296069	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-22806693	$9-87*(6-5+4^3)^2+1$
-22296213	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-22807389	$9-87*(6+5+4^3)^2-1$
-22353147	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4-3)^{21})$	-22807563	$9-87*(6+5+4^3)^2+1$
-22353291	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4-3)^{21})$	-22809042	$9-87*(6^5+4^3)^2-1$
-22354281	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4+3)^{21})$	-22809216	$9-87*(6^5+4^3)^2+1$
-22354425	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4+3)^{21})$	-22812087	$9-87*(65+4^3)^2-1$
-22413303	$-9*((87/6-5)^4)^3)^2-1$	-22812105	$-9-87*(65+4^3)^2-1$
-22413321	$-9*((87/6-5)^4)^3)^2+1$	-22812173	$9-87*(65+4^3)^2+1$
-22468599	$9-8*(7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-22812175	$9-87*(65+4^3)^2-1$
-22468617	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-22812191	$-9-87*(65+4^3)^2+1$
-22492032	$9-(87-6/5)^4)^3)^2+1$	-22812193	$-9-87*(65+4^3)^2-1$
-22573599	$9-(8*7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-22812261	$9-87*(65+4^3)^2+1$
-22573617	$-9-(8*7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-22812279	$-9-87*(65+4^3)^2+1$
-22578231	$9-8*(7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-22915728	$-9*8*(7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$
-22578249	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-22936018	$-98*((7^6-5^4-3)^2-1)$
-22584759	$9-8*(7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-22936214	$-98*((7^6-5^4-3)^2+1)$
-22586871	$9-8*(7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-22937194	$-98*((7^6-5^4+3)^2-1)$
-22586889	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-22937390	$-98*((7^6-5^4+3)^2+1)$
-22587303	$9-(8*7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-22941867	$-9*(8+7^6)^5)^4)^3)^2+1$
-22587321	$-9-(8*7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-22996386	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22587543	$9-(8*(7^6-5)^4)^3)^{21}$	-22996582	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22587735	$9-(8*(7^6-5)^4)^3)^{21}$	-23016966	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22587753	$-9-(8*(7^6-5)^4)^3)^{21}$	-23017162	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22588119	$9-(8*7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23027354	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22588359	$-9-8*(7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23027550	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22588407	$9-8*(7^6-5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23045582	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22588839	$9-8*(7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23045778	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22588857	$-9-8*(7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23047542	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22589463	$9-(8*(7^6+5)^4)^3)^{21}$	-23047738	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22589655	$9-(8*(7^6+5)^4)^3)^{21}$	-23047934	$-98*((7^6-5^4-3)^2-1)$
-22589895	$9-(8*7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23048130	$-98*((7^6-5^4-3)^2+1)$
-22589913	$-9-(8*7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23049110	$-98*((7^6-5^4+3)^2-1)$
-22589964	$9*(8-(7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23049306	$-98*((7^6-5^4+3)^2+1)$
-22590108	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23049698	$-98*((7^6-5^4-3)^2-1)$
-22590327	$9-8*(7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23049894	$-98*((7^6-5^4-3)^2+1)$
-22592439	$9-8*(7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23051658	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22598967	$9-8*(7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23051854	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22598985	$-9-8*(7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23052246	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22603599	$9-(8*7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23052442	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22603617	$-9-(8*7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23053814	$98*((-7^6+(5+4)^3)^2+1)$
-22691606	$98*((-7^6+5^4)^3)^2+1$	-23054010	$98*((-7^6+(5+4)^3)^2-1)$
-22691802	$98*((-7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$	-23054598	$-98*((7^6-5^4-3)^2-1)$
-22708599	$9-8*(7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23054794	$-98*((7^6-5^4-3)^2+1)$
-22708617	$-9-8*(7^6+5^4)^3)^{21}$	-23055578	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22764033	$9*(8-(7^6-5)^4)^3)^2+1$	-23055774	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22764051	$9*(8-(7^6-5)^4)^3)^2-1$	-23055970	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22764069	$9*((8-(7^6-5)^4)^3)^2+1$	-23057146	$98*(7^6*(5-4-3)^2+1)$
-22764087	$9*((8-(7^6-5)^4)^3)^2-1$	-23057734	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22764141	$-9*((8+(7^6-5)^4)^3)^2-1$	-23058567	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22764159	$-9*((8+(7^6-5)^4)^3)^2+1$	-23058763	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22764177	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)^4)^3)^2-1$	-23059162	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22764195	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)^4)^3)^2+1$	-23059246	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22765968	$9*(8-(7^6+5)^4)^3)^2+1$	-23059645	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22766004	$9*((8-(7^6+5)^4)^3)^2+1$	-23059841	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22766022	$9*((8-(7^6+5)^4)^3)^2-1$	-23060674	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22766076	$-9*((8+(7^6+5)^4)^3)^2-1$	-23061262	$98*(7^6*(5-4-3)^2-1)$
-22766112	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)^4)^3)^2-1$	-23062438	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22766130	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)^4)^3)^2+1$	-23062634	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22800777	$9+87*(65-4^3)^2+1$	-23062830	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22800795	$-9+87*(65-4^3)^2+1$	-23063614	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22800863	$9+87*(65-4^3)^2+1$	-23063810	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22800865	$9+87*(65-4^3)^2-1$	-23064398	$-98*((7^6+(5+4)^3)^2-1)$
-22800881	$-9+87*(65-4^3)^2+1$	-23064594	$-98*((7^6+(5+4)^3)^2+1)$
-22800883	$-9+87*(65-4^3)^2-1$	-23065966	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22800951	$9+87*(65-4^3)^2-1$	-23066162	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22800969	$-9+87*(65-4^3)^2-1$	-23066554	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22803822	$9+87*(6^5-4^3)^2+1$	-23066750	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22803996	$9+87*(6^5-4^3)^2-1$	-23069298	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22804014	$-9+87*(6^5-4^3)^2-1$	-23070278	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22805475	$9+87*(6+5-4^3)^2+1$	-23070474	$-98*((7^6+5^4)^3)^2+1$
-22805649	$9+87*(6+5-4^3)^2-1$	-23070670	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2-1$
-22806345	$9+87*(6-5-4^3)^2+1$	-23070866	$-98*((7^6-5^4)^3)^2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-23072630	$-98^*((7^6+5+4^3)^*2-1)$	-24282290	$(-9-8)^*(7^6+5^*4^3^2+1)$
-23072826	$-98^*((7^6+5+4^3)^*2+1)$	-24282358	$(-9-8)^*(7^6+5^*(4^3^2+1))$
-23090858	$-98^*((7^6+5^4)^*2-1)$	-24353226	$-9^*(8+7^6*(5^4+3))-21)$
-23091054	$-98^*((7^6+5^4)^*2+1)$	-24353245	$98-7^6*(5+4^3)^*(2+1)$
-23101246	$-98^*((7^6+5^4)^*2-1)$	-24353252	$9^*(8-7^6*(5^4+3)+2)+1$
-23101442	$-98^*((7^6+5^4)^*2+1)$	-24353254	$9^*(8-7^6*(5^4+3)+2)-1$
-23121180	$9-(87+6/5)^*(4^3^2+1)$	-24353288	$9^*(8-7^6*(5^4+3)-2)+1$
-23121198	$-9-(87+6/5)^*(4^3^2+1)$	-24353290	$9^*(8-7^6*(5^4+3)-2)-1$
-23121826	$-98^*((7^6+5^4)^*2-1)$	-24353396	$-9^*(8+7^6*(5^4+3)-2)+1$
-23122022	$-98^*((7^6+5^4)^*2+1)$	-24353398	$-9^*(8+7^6*(5^4+3)-2)-1$
-23176755	$98-7^6*(5+4^3)^*(2+1)$	-24353432	$-9^*(8+7^6*(5^4+3)+2)+1$
-23176781	$9^*8-7^6*(5+4^3)^*(2+1)$	-24353434	$-9^*(8+7^6*(5^4+3)+2)-1$
-23176925	$9^*-8-7^6*(5+4^3)^*(2+1)$	-24353441	$-98-7^6*(5+4^3)^*(2+1)$
-23176951	$-98-7^6*(5+4^3)^*(2+1)$	-24353604	$-9^*(8+7^6*(5^4+3)+21)$
-23181018	$-98^*((7^6+5^4-3)^*2-1)$	-24378825	$9+(87+6)^*(5-4^3^2+1)$
-23181214	$-98^*((7^6+5^4-3)^*2+1)$	-24379011	$9+(87+6)^*(5-4^3^2-1)$
-23182194	$-98^*((7^6+5^4+3)^*2-1)$	-24379755	$9-(87+6)^*(5+4^3^2-1)$
-23182390	$-98^*((7^6+5^4+3)^*2+1)$	-24379941	$9-(87+6)^*(5+4^3^2+1)$
-23293440	$9^*(8-(7^6-5)^*(43-21))$	-24452022	$98-7^*(6-5^4^3)^2-1)$
-23293584	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5)^*(43-21))$	-24452036	$98-7^*(6-5^4^3)^2+1)$
-23294421	$9^*(8-7^6*(54-32)+1)$	-24452048	$9^*8-7^*(6-5^4^3)^2-1)$
-23294439	$9^*(8-7^6*(54-32)-1)$	-24452062	$9^*8-7^*(6-5^4^3)^2+1)$
-23294565	$-9^*(8+7^6*(54-32)-1)$	-24452192	$9^*-8-7^*(6-5^4^3)^2-1)$
-23294583	$-9^*(8+7^6*(54-32)+1)$	-24452206	$9^*-8-7^*(6-5^4^3)^2+1)$
-23295420	$9^*(8-(7^6+5)^*(43-21))$	-24452218	$-98-7^*(6-5^4^3)^2-1)$
-23295564	$-9^*(8+(7^6+5)^*(43-21))$	-24452232	$-98-7^*(6-5^4^3)^2+1)$
-23330896	$9-(8+76+5)^*(4^3^2+1)$	-24484065	$(-9/(8+7^6*(5^4*3-2)))^{\wedge-1}$
-23426606	$-98^*((7^6+5^4)^*2-1)$	-24504312	$-98^*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-23426802	$-98^*((7^6+5^4)^*2+1)$	-24504508	$-98^*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
-23442104	$(9/8/-7^*(6^5/4-3))^{\wedge-2}$	-24504704	$-98^*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
-23482944	$9-87^*(6^5+4^3^2-1)$	-24504900	$-98^*((7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
-23482962	$-9-87^*(6^5+4^3^2-1)$	-24538021	$(-9/((8+7^6)^*(5^4*3+2)))^{\wedge-1}$
-23483118	$9-87^*(6^5+4^3^2+1)$	-24608924	$9^*(8+7^*(6-5^4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$
-23483136	$-9-87^*(6^5+4^3^2+1)$	-24608926	$9^*(8+7^*(6-5^4^{\wedge}(3/2))))-1$
-23529390	$(9+(8-7^6*5)^*4)^*(3^2+1)$	-24609068	$-9^*(8-7^*(6-5^4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$
-23529570	$(-9+(8-7^6*5)^*4)^*(3^2+1)$	-24609070	$-9^*(8-7^*(6-5^4^{\wedge}(3/2))))-1$
-23529675	$-9^*(8+7^6*5)^*((4/3)^2+1)$	-24609680	$9^*(8-7^*(6+5^4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$
-23529702	$98-7^6*5^*(43-2-1)$	-24609682	$9^*(8-7^*(6+5^4^{\wedge}(3/2))))-1$
-23529898	$-98-7^6*5^*(43-2-1)$	-24609824	$-9^*(8+7^*(6+5^4^{\wedge}(3/2))))+1$
-23530030	$(9-(8+7^6*5)^*4)^*(3^2+1)$	-24609826	$-9^*(8+7^*(6+5^4^{\wedge}(3/2))))-1$
-23530210	$(9+(8+7^6*5)^*4)^*(3^2-1)$	-24627106	$-98^*((7^6+(5^4)^3)^*2-1)$
-23587256	$(9/8/-7^*(6^5/4+3))^{\wedge-2}$	-24627302	$-98^*((7^6+(5^4)^3)^*2+1)$
-23646372	$9^*(8-(7^6-5)^*(4/3+21))$	-24662799	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5^4/3^*2+1)$
-23646516	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5)^*(4/3+21))$	-24702174	$(98-7^6*5)^*(43-2+1)$
-23648382	$9^*(8-(7^6+5)^*(4/3+21))$	-24705777	$9-8^*(7^6*5/4-3)^*21$
-23648526	$-9^*(8+(7^6+5)^*(4/3+21))$	-24705945	$9+(8-7^6*5)^*(43-2+1)$
-23747589	$9^*(8-(7^6+(5^4)^3)^*21)$	-24706192	$98-7^6*5^*(43-2+1)$
-23747733	$-9^*(8+(7^6+(5^4)^3)^*21)$	-24706388	$-98-7^6*5^*(43-2+1)$
-23765089	$9-8^*7^6*(5/4+3+21)$	-24706617	$9-(8+7^6*5)^*(43-2+1)$
-23822982	$-9^*(8+(7^6-5)^*(43/2+1))$	-24706626	$-9^*(8+7^6*5)^*(4+(3/2))^{\wedge-1}$
-23824863	$9^*(8-(7^6+5)^*(43/2+1))$	-24706785	$9-8^*(7^6*5/4+3)^*21$
-23825007	$-9^*(8+(7^6+5)^*(43/2+1))$	-24710406	$(98+7^6*5)^*(-43+2-1)$
-23849098	$(98-7)^*(65-4^3^2+1)$	-24767022	$98-7^*(6+5^4^3)^2-1)$
-23849280	$(98-7)^*(65-4^3^2-1)$	-24767036	$98-7^*(6+5^4^3)^2+1)$
-23860928	$(-98+7)^*(65+4^3^2-1)$	-24767048	$9^*8-7^*(6+5^4^3)^2-1)$
-23861110	$(-98+7)^*(65+4^3^2+1)$	-24767062	$9^*8-7^*(6+5^4^3)^2+1)$
-23892544	$(-9/(8^*(7^6-5^4)^3))^{\wedge-1}$	-24767192	$-9^*8-7^*(6+5^4^3)^2-1)$
-23999325	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5)^*4^3-2-1)$	-24767206	$-9^*8-7^*(6+5^4^3)^2+1)$
-23999359	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5)^*4^3-2+1)$	-24767218	$-98-7^*(6+5^4^3)^2-1)$
-23999393	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5)^*4^3+2-1)$	-24903110	$(-9+8^*(7+6))^*(5-4^3^2+1)$
-23999427	$(-9-8)^*((7^6-5)^*4^3+2+1)$	-24903300	$(-9+8^*(7+6))^*(5-4^3^2-1)$
-24000298	$98-7^6*5^*(43-2-1)$	-24927280	$98^*(7+6^5-4^3^2+1)$
-24000494	$-98-7^6*5^*(43-2-1)$	-24927476	$98^*(7+6^5-4^3^2-1)$
-24001365	$(-9-8)^*((7^6+5)^*4^3-2-1)$	-24928652	$-98^*(7-6^5+4^3^2-1)$
-24001399	$(-9-8)^*((7^6+5)^*4^3-2+1)$	-24928848	$-98^*(7-6^5+4^3^2+1)$
-24001433	$(-9-8)^*((7^6+5)^*4^3+2-1)$	-24941490	$98-7^6*5^*(5^4*3-2-1)$
-24001467	$(-9-8)^*((7^6+5)^*4^3+2+1)$	-24941686	$-98-7^6*5^*(5^4*3-2-1)$
-24039409	$(-9/(8/(7^6+5^4+3))^{\wedge-2})^{\wedge-1}$	-25008816	$-9^*8^*7^6*(5-43/21)$
-24235596	$98-7^6*5^*(43-2+1)$	-25159488	$(9+87)^*(65-4^3^2+1)$
-24235792	$-98-7^6*5^*(43-2+1)$	-25159680	$(9+87)^*(65-4^3^2-1)$
-24282188	$(-9-8)^*(7^6+5^*(4^3^2-1))$	-25171968	$(-9-87)^*(65+4^3^2-1)$
-24282256	$(-9-8)^*(7^6+5^*(4^3^2+1))$	-25172160	$(-9-87)^*(65+4^3^2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-25176788	$98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5 \cdot 43 - 2 + 1)$	-25422336	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 + 54) \cdot 3 - 21)$
-25176984	$-98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5 \cdot 43 - 2 + 1)$	-25423659	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) \cdot 3 - 21)$
-25240575	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7 - 6 + 5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-25424037	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 + 54) \cdot 3 + 21)$
-25240577	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7 - 6 + 5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-25425360	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 + 54) \cdot 3 + 21)$
-25277112	$9 \cdot (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot (3 + 21))$	-25426845	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 + 543) \cdot (2 + 1)$
-25277256	$-9 \cdot (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot (3 + 21))$	-25428870	$-9 \cdot ((8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 21)$
-25280783	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7/6 + 5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-25429248	$-9 \cdot ((8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 + 21)$
-25280785	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7/6 + 5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-25515836	$(-9 / (876 \cdot (5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)))^{\wedge} - 1$
-25294896	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 - 543) \cdot (2 + 1)$	-25529472	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 + 543) \cdot (2 + 1)$
-25395120	$9 \cdot ((-8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 + 21)$	-25545672	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 21)$
-25395498	$9 \cdot ((-8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 21)$	-25546995	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 21)$
-25397523	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 - 543) \cdot (2 + 1)$	-25547373	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 + 21)$
-25399008	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 54) \cdot 3 - 21)$	-25548696	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 + 21)$
-25400331	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) \cdot 3 - 21)$	-25645424	$98 \cdot (7 \cdot 65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25400493	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) \cdot 3 - 2 - 1)$	-25645521	$98 \cdot (7 \cdot 65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-25400556	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 54) \cdot 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	-25645523	$98 \cdot (7 \cdot 65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-25400655	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 54) \cdot 3 + 2) - 1)$	-25645620	$98 \cdot (7 \cdot 65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25400709	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 - 54) \cdot 3 + 21)$	-25647384	$98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5 \cdot 43 + 2 + 1)$
-25400736	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 54) \cdot 3 + 2 + 1)$	-25647580	$-98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5 \cdot 43 + 2 + 1)$
-25402032	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 54) \cdot 3 + 21)$	-25661979	$(-98 + 7/65) \cdot (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25407719	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 3 + 2) + 1$	-25682468	$98 \cdot (7 \cdot (6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25407721	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 3 + 2) - 1$	-25682664	$98 \cdot (7 \cdot (6 + 5) - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25407783	$9 \cdot (8 \cdot (-7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) + 3) \cdot (2 + 1)$	-25682958	$98 \cdot (7 + 65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25407845	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 2) + 1$	-25683644	$98 \cdot ((7 + 6) \cdot 5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25407847	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 2) - 1$	-25683840	$98 \cdot ((7 + 6) \cdot 5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25407881	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 + 2) + 1$	-25684330	$-98 \cdot (7 - 65 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25407883	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 + 2) - 1$	-25684526	$-98 \cdot (7 - 65 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25407945	$9 \cdot (8 \cdot (-7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) - 3) \cdot (2 + 1)$	-25685408	$98 \cdot (7 \cdot 6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25408007	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 3 - 2) + 1$	-25685604	$98 \cdot (7 \cdot 6 + 5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25408009	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 3 - 2) - 1$	-25687760	$-98 \cdot (7 - 6 \cdot 5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25409832	$(98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5 + 4)) \cdot (3 + 21)$	-25687956	$-98 \cdot (7 - 6 \cdot 5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25410051	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) \cdot 3 - 21)$	-25689818	$-98 \cdot (7 - 6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25410537	$-9 \cdot ((8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 - 54) \cdot 3 - 21)$	-25690005	$9 \cdot (87 + 6 + 5) \cdot (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25410780	$9 \cdot (8 \cdot (-7^{\wedge}6 + 5) + 4 \cdot 3) \cdot (2 + 1)$	-25690028	$-98 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 - (6 + 5) + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25410959	$9 \cdot (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3) \cdot 2 + 1$	-25690201	$9 \cdot (87 + 6 + 5) \cdot (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25410961	$9 \cdot (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3) \cdot 2 - 1$	-25690224	$-98 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 - (6 + 5) + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25411031	$9 \cdot (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2) + 1$	-25690308	$-98 \cdot ((7 - 6)^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25411033	$9 \cdot (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2) - 1$	-25690994	$-98 \cdot (7 + 6 - 5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25411175	$-9 \cdot (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2) + 1$	-25691778	$-98 \cdot (7 + 6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25411177	$-9 \cdot (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2) - 1$	-25691974	$-98 \cdot (7 + 6 + 5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25411247	$9 \cdot (-8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3) \cdot 2 + 1$	-25695698	$98 \cdot (7 - 65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25411249	$9 \cdot (-8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3) \cdot 2 - 1$	-25695894	$98 \cdot (7 - 65 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25411428	$9 \cdot (8 \cdot (-7^{\wedge}6 + 5) - 4 \cdot 3) \cdot (2 + 1)$	-25697266	$-98 \cdot (7 + 65 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25411792	$(98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 54) \cdot (3 + 2 - 1)$	-25710594	$-98 \cdot (7 \cdot 6 \cdot 5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25411983	$9 + (8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5 + 4)) \cdot (3 + 21)$	-25710790	$-98 \cdot (7 \cdot 6 \cdot 5 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25412143	$9 + (8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 54) \cdot (3 + 2 - 1)$	-25718441	$(-98 - 7/65) \cdot (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25412207	$9 \cdot (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 54) \cdot (3 + 2 - 1)$	-25734604	$-98 \cdot (7 \cdot 65 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25412385	$-9 \cdot (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5 + 4)) \cdot (3 + 21)$	-25734701	$-98 \cdot (7 \cdot 65 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-25412576	$(98 + 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 54) \cdot (-3 - 2 + 1)$	-25734703	$-98 \cdot (7 \cdot 65 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-25412940	$9 \cdot (-8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) + 4 \cdot 3) \cdot (2 + 1)$	-25734800	$-98 \cdot (7 \cdot 65 + 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25413119	$9 \cdot (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3) \cdot 2 + 1$	-25828065	$((9^{\wedge}8 - 7 + 6) / -5 - 4) \cdot 3 - 21$
-25413121	$9 \cdot (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3) \cdot 2 - 1$	-25878468	$(98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5) \cdot (43 + 2 - 1)$
-25413191	$9 \cdot (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2) + 1$	-25882419	$9 + (8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5) \cdot (43 + 2 - 1)$
-25413193	$9 \cdot (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2) - 1$	-25882682	$98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5 \cdot (43 + 2 - 1)$
-25413335	$-9 \cdot (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2) + 1$	-25882878	$-98 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5 \cdot (43 + 2 - 1)$
-25413337	$-9 \cdot (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2) - 1$	-25883123	$9 \cdot (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5) \cdot (43 + 2 - 1)$
-25413407	$9 \cdot (-8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3) \cdot 2 + 1$	-25887092	$(98 + 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5) \cdot (-43 - 2 + 1)$
-25413409	$9 \cdot (-8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) \cdot 4 \cdot 3) \cdot 2 - 1$	-25898589	$((9^{\wedge}8 + 7^{\wedge}6) / -5 - 4) \cdot 3 + 21$
-25413588	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) + 4 \cdot 3) \cdot (2 + 1)$	-25898655	$((9^{\wedge}8 + 7^{\wedge}6) / -5 - 4) \cdot 3 - 21$
-25413831	$-9 \cdot ((8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6 + 54) \cdot 3 + 21)$	-25940404	$-98 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25413966	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5/4) \cdot 3 + 21)$	-25940600	$-98 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25414536	$(98 + 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot (5 + 4)) \cdot (-3 - 21)$	-25942609	$-98 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) / 4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25416359	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 3 + 2) + 1$	-25942805	$-98 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) / 4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-25416361	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 3 + 2) - 1$	-25951751	$9 \cdot (8 \cdot 7 - (6 + 5) \cdot 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-25416423	$9 \cdot (-8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) + 3) \cdot (2 + 1)$	-25951753	$9 \cdot (8 \cdot 7 - (6 + 5) \cdot 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-25416485	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 2) + 1$	-25952122	$9 \cdot (8 + 7 - (6 + 5) \cdot 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-25416487	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 2) - 1$	-25952390	$-9 \cdot (8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \cdot 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-25416521	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 + 2) + 1$	-25952392	$-9 \cdot (8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \cdot 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-25416523	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 + 2) - 1$	-25952759	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot 7 + (6 + 5) \cdot 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-25416585	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) + 3) \cdot (2 + 1)$	-25952761	$-9 \cdot (8 \cdot 7 + (6 + 5) \cdot 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-25416647	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 3 - 2) + 1$	-25952940	$-9 \cdot (87 + (6 + 5) \cdot 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-25416649	$9 \cdot 8 \cdot ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) \cdot 3 - 3 - 2) - 1$	-25953030	$-9 \cdot (87 + (6 + 5) \cdot 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-25953048	$-9*(87+(6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-27293399	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-32-1)$
-25953138	$-9*(87+(6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-27294704	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-32-1)$
-25999307	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(-4-3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-27295719	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-32-1)$
-25999341	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(-4-3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-27295873	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6/5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-26000412	$(-9-8)*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1$	-27367929	$9-87*6/5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-26000446	$(-9-8)*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3/2))+1$	-27518190	$(98+7)*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-26001517	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(-4-3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-27518400	$(98+7)*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-26001551	$(9+8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(-4-3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-27531840	$(-98-7)*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-26214265	$(9-8^{\wedge}7/(6/5))*4^{\wedge}(3+2+1)$	-27532050	$(-98-7)*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-26214535	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7/(6/5))*4^{\wedge}(3+2+1)$	-27662944	$(-9-8)/(7/((6+5+4)^{\wedge}(3*2)-1))$
-26265816	$(-9-8)*((7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-27692352	$-9*(8^{\wedge}7+6^{\wedge}(5+4-3)*21)$
-26265850	$(-9-8)*((7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-27825957	$(9+8)*7^{\wedge}6*-5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-26313937	$(9-8*7)*6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)*2-1$	-27999255	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-26314031	$(9-8*7)*6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)*2+1$	-27999289	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-26352239	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-32)+1)$	-28000453	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5/4-32+1)$
-26352255	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-32)-1)$	-28001635	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-26352257	$-9+8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-32)+1)$	-28001669	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-26354479	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-32)+1)$	-28079920	$-98*((7/(6*5^{\wedge}4-3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
-26354495	$9+8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-32)-1)$	-28119519	$9*(8*(76-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))+1)$
-26451376	$98*(7-6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-28119537	$9*(8*(76-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1)$
-26451572	$98*(7-6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-28130463	$-9*(8*(76+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1)$
-26452748	$-98*(7+6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-28217343	$-9*(8*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2+1$
-26453854	$98-7*(6^{\wedge}5/4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$	-28217345	$-9*(8*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2-1$
-26453879	$9*(8-7*(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-28227968	$-9*(8*(7+6)-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-26453881	$9*(8-7*(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	-28227970	$-9/(8*(7+6)-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-26454023	$-9*(8+7*(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-28235662	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-26454025	$-9*(8+7*(6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	-28235858	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*5*((4+3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-26454050	$-98-7*(6^{\wedge}5/4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1)$	-28236144	$(-9/((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*432))^{\wedge}2-1$
-26470772	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*3+2)+1$	-28259857	$-9*(8+(7*6)^{\wedge}(-5+4+3))^{\wedge}2-1$
-26470774	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*3+2)-1$	-28575513	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-26470916	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*3+2)+1$	-28575657	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-26470918	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*3+2)-1$	-28579707	$-9*((87+6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-26471132	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*3+2)+1$	-28579725	$-9*((87+6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-26471134	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*3+2)-1$	-28587420	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-32+1))$
-26471276	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*3+2)+1$	-28587564	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-32+1))$
-26471278	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*3+2)-1$	-28588302	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))*3+21)$
-26561888	$9*(8-76)*((5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-28588446	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)*3+21)$
-26562423	$9*(8-76)*((5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-28588472	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))*3+2)+1$
-26562441	$-9+(8-76)*((5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-28588474	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))*3+2)-1$
-26562559	$9+(8-76)*((5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-28588508	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))*3-2)+1$
-26588576	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(43+2)+1$	-28588510	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))*3-2)-1$
-26588772	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(43+2)+1$	-28588590	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)*3-21)$
-26738658	$-9*8^{\wedge}7-6*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-28588904	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))*3+2)+1$
-26738671	$(-9-8)*((7-6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-28588906	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))*3+2)-1$
-26738682	$-9*8^{\wedge}7-6*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-28588940	$-9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))*3+2)+1$
-26738694	$-9*8^{\wedge}7-6*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-28588942	$-9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))*3+2)-1$
-26738705	$(-9-8)*((7-6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-28588968	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)*3+21)$
-26738718	$-9*8^{\wedge}7-6*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-28589850	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-32+1))$
-26751550	$98*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	-28589994	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-32+1))$
-26751746	$98*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	-28601757	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+54)*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-26775888	$9*(8-(7+65^{\wedge}4/3)/2+1)$	-28601829	$9^{\wedge}8-8*(7^{\wedge}6+54)*3^{\wedge}21$
-26775987	$9*(-8+(7-65^{\wedge}4/3)/2-1)$	-28601901	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+54)*3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-26776050	$-9*(8+(7+65^{\wedge}4/3)/2+1)$	-28706258	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-26823955	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)/2-1)$	-28706284	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-26823989	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)/2+1)$	-28706428	$9*-8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-26843542	$(9-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)*4)/(3/2+1)$	-28706454	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-26860816	$(-9-8)*((7+6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-28810775	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*3(2+1)$
-26860850	$(-9-8)*((7+6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-28820771	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
-26982663	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6)*5^{\wedge}4/3+21$	-28820967	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$
-26982681	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6)*5^{\wedge}4/3+21$	-28821996	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6*5-43)/2+1)$
-27003312	$(98+7^{\wedge}6)*5^{\wedge}4/3-21$	-28822682	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-3/2)-1)$
-27054762	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43+2+1)$	-28822878	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-3/2)+1)$
-27058893	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43+2+1)$	-28823870	$(-98*7^{\wedge}6+54)*3(2+1)$
-27058911	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43+2+1)$	-28824140	$(-98*7^{\wedge}6-54)*3(2+1)$
-27059172	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(43+2+1)$	-28825132	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-3/2)-1)$
-27059368	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(43+2+1)$	-28825328	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-3/2)+1)$
-27059629	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43+2+1)$	-28826014	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6*5+43)/2-1)$
-27059647	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43+2+1)$	-28827043	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
-27063778	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(-43-2-1)$	-28827239	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$
-27083565	$9*(8+7)*6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3^{\wedge}21)$	-28837235	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+54)*3(2+1)$
-27085185	$-9*(8+7)*6^{\wedge}(5+4*3^{\wedge}21)$	-28941556	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-27293263	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6/5)*((4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-28941582	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3)^{\wedge}2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-28941726	$9^* - 8 \cdot 7^{\wedge}6^* (5^* (4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-30000308	$(-9-8) * ((7^{\wedge}6^*5-4) * 3+2-1)$
-28941752	$-98 - 7^{\wedge}6^* (5^* (4+3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-30000427	$(9+8) * (7^{\wedge}6^* -5+4/3) * (2+1)$
-29021943	$9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (32-1)$	-30000478	$(9+8) * (7^{\wedge}6^* (-5-4-3^*2)+1)$
-29021961	$-9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (32-1)$	-30000512	$(-9-8) * (7^{\wedge}6^* (5+4^*3-2)+1)$
-29059205	$98+7^{\wedge}6^* (5-4^*3^*21)$	-30000563	$(9+8) * (7^{\wedge}6^*5+4/3) * (-2-1)$
-29059401	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^* (5-4^*3^*21)$	-30000682	$(-9-8) * ((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4) * 3-2+1)$
-29157568	$9 - (8^*7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (32-1)$	-30000716	$(-9-8) * ((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4) * 3+2-1)$
-29157586	$-9 - (8^*7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (32-1)$	-30000750	$(-9-8) * ((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4) * 3+2+1)$
-29163551	$9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (32-1)$	-30001107	$(9+8) * (7^{\wedge}6^*5+4^*3) * (-2-1)$
-29163569	$-9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (32-1)$	-30013308	$9^{\wedge}8 - 7^{\wedge}6^* (5^{\wedge}4 - 3 - 2 + 1)$
-29171983	$9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4) * (32-1)$	-30015751	$9^* - 8 / ((7 - 6^{\wedge}5/4) / 3)^{\wedge} - 2 + 1$
-29174711	$9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * (32-1)$	-30015753	$9^* - 8 / ((7 - 6^{\wedge}5/4) / 3)^{\wedge} - 2 - 1$
-29175269	$9 - (8^*7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * (32-1)$	-30104303	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 - 1)$
-29175579	$9 - (8^* (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) - 4) * (32 - 1)$	-30104319	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 + 1)$
-29175827	$9 - (8^* (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) + 4) * (32 - 1)$	-30104321	$-9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 - 1)$
-29176633	$9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 - 5/4) * (32 - 1)$	-30104337	$-9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 + 1)$
-29176695	$9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * (32 - 1)$	-30113007	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^*4) * 32 - 1)$
-29177191	$9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * (32 - 1)$	-30113023	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4) * 32 + 1)$
-29177222	$9 - (8^*7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * (32 - 1)$	-30115823	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 32 - 1)$
-29177253	$9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 + 5/4) * (32 - 1)$	-30115839	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 32 + 1)$
-29178059	$9 - (8^* (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) - 4) * (32 - 1)$	-30115857	$-9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 32 + 1)$
-29178307	$9 - (8^* (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) + 4) * (32 - 1)$	-30117807	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5/4) * 32 - 1)$
-29178617	$9 - (8^*7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 - 1)$	-30117871	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * 32 - 1)$
-29178635	$-9 - (8^*7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 - 1)$	-30118056	$(9 + (8/7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4) * (-3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-29179175	$9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * (32 - 1)$	-30118383	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * 32 - 1)$
-29181903	$9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4) * (32 - 1)$	-30118447	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5/4) * 32 - 1)$
-29190335	$9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 - 1)$	-30118481	$-9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5/4) * 32 + 1)$
-29190353	$-9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 - 1)$	-30120431	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * 32 - 1)$
-29196318	$9 - (8^*7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 - 1)$	-30120447	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * 32 + 1)$
-29196336	$-9 - (8^*7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 - 1)$	-30123247	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4) * 32 - 1)$
-29294529	$9^* (8 - 7^{\wedge}6^* (5^*4/3+21))$	-30123263	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^*4) * 32 + 1)$
-29294673	$-9^* (8 + 7^{\wedge}6^* (5^*4/3+21))$	-30131951	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 - 1)$
-29331943	$9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 - 1)$	-30131967	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 + 1)$
-29331961	$-9 - 8^* (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * (32 - 1)$	-30131969	$-9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5/4) * 32 - 1)$
-29513737	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^{\wedge}6) * (-5/4/32+1)$	-30131985	$-9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 + 1)$
-29529801	$98+7^{\wedge}6^* (5-4^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$	-30235695	$98 - 7^{\wedge}6^* (5+4^*3^*21)$
-29529997	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^* (5-4^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$	-30235891	$-98 - 7^{\wedge}6^* (5+4^*3^*21)$
-29644230	$(98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4^*3) * 21$	-30238928	$9^* (8 - (7^*6 - 5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-29645490	$(98 - 7^{\wedge}6^* (5+4+3)) * 21$	-30238930	$9^* (8 - (7^*6 - 5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-29645775	$9 + (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4) * 3^*21$	-30239072	$-9^* (8 + (7^*6 - 5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2) + 1$
-29646111	$9 + (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4^*3) * 21$	-30239074	$-9^* (8 + (7^*6 - 5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2) - 1$
-29646129	$-9 + (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4^*3) * 21$	-30248606	$9^{\wedge}8 - 7^{\wedge}6^* (5^{\wedge}4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$
-29646190	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4^*3^*21$	-30269775	$(9+8) * (7^* (6^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1)$
-29646207	$9^* (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 - 32) + 1)$	-30269809	$(9+8) * (7^* (6^{\wedge}5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1)$
-29646369	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 - 32) - 1)$	-30278127	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 - 1)$
-29646386	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4^*3^*21$	-30278143	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 + 1)$
-29646447	$9 - (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4^*3) * 21$	-30278145	$-9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 - 1)$
-29646750	$(98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4^*3) * 21$	-30278161	$-9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 + 1)$
-29647371	$9 + (8 - 7^{\wedge}6^* (5+4+3)) * 21$	-30353433	$9 - 8^* 7^{\wedge}6^* (5/4+32-1)$
-29647389	$-9 + (8 - 7^{\wedge}6^* (5+4+3)) * 21$	-30451191	$9 - 8^* ((76+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-29647707	$9 - (8+7^{\wedge}6^* (5+4+3)) * 21$	-30451207	$9 - 8^* ((76+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-29647725	$-9 - (8+7^{\wedge}6^* (5+4+3)) * 21$	-30451209	$-9 - 8^* ((76+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-29648346	$(98 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4^*3) * -21$	-30451225	$-9 - 8^* ((76+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-29648631	$9 + (8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4^*3) * 21$	-30635150	$98 - (7 / ((6+5)^{\wedge}4 + 3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge} - 1$
-29648710	$98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4^*3^*21$	-30635176	$9^* 8 - (7 / ((6+5)^{\wedge}4 + 3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge} - 1$
-29648889	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 - 32) - 1)$	-30635320	$-9^* 8 - (7 / ((6+5)^{\wedge}4 + 3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge} - 1$
-29648906	$-98 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4^*3^*21$	-30635346	$-98 - (7 / ((6+5)^{\wedge}4 + 3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge} - 1$
-29648967	$9 - (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4^*3) * 21$	-30670192	$9^* (8 + (7+6) * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)) - 1$
-29649303	$9 - (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4) * 3^*21$	-30670334	$9^* (-8 + (7+6) * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)) + 1$
-29649606	$(98 + 7^{\wedge}6^* (5+4+3)) * -21$	-30670336	$9^* (-8 + (7+6) * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)) - 1$
-29650866	$(98 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4^*3) * -21$	-30670722	$9 - (87+6^*5) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-29660361	$9^{\wedge}8 - 7^{\wedge}6^* (5^{\wedge}4 - 3^*2 - 1)$	-30670956	$9 - (87+6^*5) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-29882837	$9+8^*7^{\wedge}6^* (5/4-32-1)$	-30671362	$9^* (8 - (7+6) * (5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)) - 1$
-29958127	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 - 1)$	-30671504	$-9^* (8 + (7+6) * (5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)) + 1$
-29958143	$9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 + 1)$	-30671506	$-9^* (8 + (7+6) * (5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)) - 1$
-29958145	$-9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 - 1)$	-30705012	$9^* (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 - 32 - 1))$
-29958161	$-9 - 8^* ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5^{\wedge}4) * 32 + 1)$	-30705156	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 - 32 - 1))$
-29972271	$-98^* (7/6^* (5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1)$	-30706291	$98 - 7^{\wedge}6^* (5+4^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$
-29972467	$-98^* (7/6^* (5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1)$	-30706487	$-98 - 7^{\wedge}6^* (5+4^{\wedge}(3+2-1))$
-29999883	$(9+8) * (7^{\wedge}6^* - 5+4^*3) * (2+1)$	-30707622	$9^* (8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 - 32 - 1))$
-30000240	$(-9-8) * ((7^{\wedge}6^*5-4) * 3-2-1)$	-30707766	$9^* (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * (4 - 32 - 1))$
-30000274	$(-9-8) * ((7^{\wedge}6^*5-4) * 3-2+1)$	-30719202	$9^{\wedge}8 - 7^{\wedge}6^* (5^{\wedge}4 + 3 - 2 + 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-30719981	$9^*((8^{(7/-6)}/5)^{-4/-3+2})+1$	-31437946	$9^*(8^*7-(6-5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-30719983	$9^*((8^{(7/-6)}/5)^{-4/-3+2})-1$	-31438313	$9^*(8+7-(6-5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-30720017	$-9^*((8^{(7/-6)}/5)^{-4/3+2})+1$	-31438315	$9^*(8+7-(6-5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-30720019	$-9^*((8^{(7/-6)}/5)^{-4/3+2})-1$	-31438439	$9^*(8-7-(6-5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-30827566	$98^*(7-6/5*(4^{43^2+1}))$	-31438441	$9^*(8-7-(6-5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-30828938	$-98^*(7+6/5*(4^{43^2+1}))$	-31438457	$-9^*(8-7+(6-5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-30876608	$-9/((8*(7-6^{(-5+4)}))^{\wedge-3/21})$	-31438459	$-9^*(8-7+(6-5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-30894327	$9-8^*(7^{46-5^{44}})^*(32+1)$	-31438583	$-9^*(8+7+(6-5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-30894345	$-9-8^*(7^{46-5^{44}})^*(32+1)$	-31438585	$-9^*(8+7+(6-5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-30954500	$9^{48-7^{46}}*(5^{44+3+2}-1)$	-31438952	$-9^*(8^*7+(6-5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-31038702	$9-(8^*7^{46-5^{44}})^*(32+1)$	-31438954	$-9^*(8^*7+(6-5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-31038720	$-9-(8^*7^{46-5^{44}})^*(32+1)$	-31439223	$-9^*(87+(6-5^{4*3})^2-1)$
-31045071	$9-8^*(7^{46-54})^*(32+1)$	-31439241	$-9^*(87+(6-5^{4*3})^2+1)$
-31045089	$-9-8^*(7^{46-54})^*(32+1)$	-31458045	$-9^*((8^{47}/(6/5)+43)^*2-1)$
-31054047	$9-8^*(7^{46-5^4})^*(32+1)$	-31606811	$9^*(8-(7-6-5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-31056951	$9-8^*(7^{46-5-4})^*(32+1)$	-31606813	$9^*(8-(7-6-5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-31056969	$-9-8^*(7^{46-5-4})^*(32+1)$	-31606955	$-9^*(8+(7-6-5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-31057545	$-9-(8^*7^{46-54})^*(32+1)$	-31606957	$-9^*(8+(7-6-5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-31057563	$-9-(8^*7^{46-54})^*(32+1)$	-31664316	$9^*(8-7^{46}*(5^{44+3})/21)$
-31057875	$9-(8^*(7^{46-5}-4))^*(32+1)$	-31664460	$-9^*(8+7^{46}*(5^{44+3})/21)$
-31058139	$9-(8^*(7^{46-5}+4))^*(32+1)$	-31674311	$9^*(8-(7-6+5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-31058157	$-9-(8^*(7^{46-5}+4))^*(32+1)$	-31674313	$9^*(8-(7-6+5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-31058667	$9-(8^*7^{46-5^4})^*(32+1)$	-31674455	$-9^*(8+(7-6+5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-31058997	$9-8^*(7^{46-5/4})^*(32+1)$	-31674457	$-9^*(8+(7-6+5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-31059063	$9-8^*(7^{46-5+4})^*(32+1)$	-31719294	$9-(8^*7+65)^*(4^{43^2}-1)$
-31059147	$-9^*(8^*7^{46}*(5-4/3)-21)$	-31719536	$9-(8^*7+65)^*(4^{43^2+1})$
-31059317	$-9^*(8^*7^{46}*(5-4/3)-2)+1$	-31719554	$-9-(8^*7+65)^*(4^{43^2+1})$
-31059355	$-9^*(8^*7^{46}*(5-4/3)+2)-1$	-31764941	$9^*(8-(7^{46}*(5-4)^3)^2)+1$
-31059360	$9-(8^*7^{46+5-4})^*(32+1)$	-31764943	$9^*(8-(7^{46}*(5-4)^3)^2)-1$
-31059591	$-9-8^*(7^{46+5-4})^*(32+1)$	-31764987	$(9-8^*7^{46}*(5/4))^3*(2+1)$
-31059624	$9-(8^*7^{46+5+4})^*(32+1)$	-31765473	$(-9-8^*7^{46}*(5/4))^3*(2+1)$
-31059657	$9-8^*(7^{46+5/4})^*(32+1)$	-31765517	$-9^*(8+(7^{46}*(5+4)^3)^2)+1$
-31059675	$-9-8^*(7^{46+5/4})^*(32+1)$	-31765519	$-9^*(8+(7^{46}*(5+4)^3)^2)-1$
-31060515	$9-(8^*(7^{46+5}-4))^*(32+1)$	-31842657	$9^*(87-(6+5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-31060779	$9-(8^*(7^{46+5}+4))^*(32+1)$	-31842675	$9^*(87-(6+5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-31060848	$-9-8^*(7^{46}*(5-4/3)+21)$	-31842944	$9^*(8^*7-(6+5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-31061109	$9-(8^*7^{46+54})^*(32+1)$	-31842946	$9^*(8^*7-(6+5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-31061127	$-9-(8^*7^{46+54})^*(32+1)$	-31843313	$9^*(8+7-(6+5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-31061703	$9-8^*(7^{46+5+4})^*(32+1)$	-31843315	$9^*(8+7-(6+5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-31064607	$9-8^*(7^{46+5^4})^*(32+1)$	-31843583	$-9^*(8+7+(6+5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-31073583	$9-8^*(7^{46+54})^*(32+1)$	-31843585	$-9^*(8+7+(6+5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-31073601	$-9-8^*(7^{46+54})^*(32+1)$	-31843952	$-9^*(8^*7+(6+5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-31079952	$9-(8^*7^{46+5^{44}})^*(32+1)$	-31843954	$-9^*(8^*7+(6+5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-31079970	$-9-(8^*7^{46+5^{44}})^*(32+1)$	-31844223	$-9^*(87+(6+5^{4*3})^2-1)$
-31191549	$(9+8)^*(7*(6^5-4^{43^2})+1)$	-31844241	$-9^*(87+(6+5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-31191583	$(9+8)^*(7*(6^5-4^{43^2})-1)$	-31876823	$9-8^*7^{46}*(5/4)^3*(2+1)$
-31193810	$(9+8)^*(7*(6+5-4^{43^2})+1)$	-31933800	$-9/((87^*65-4)/3)^{\wedge-2+1}$
-31193844	$(9+8)^*(7*(6+5-4^{43^2})-1)$	-31933802	$-9/((87^*65-4)/3)^{\wedge-2-1}$
-31195000	$(9+8)^*(7*(6-5-4^{43^2})+1)$	-31957800	$-98^*(7^{46}*(5-4^{43^2})-1)$
-31195034	$(9+8)^*(7*(6-5-4^{43^2})-1)$	-31957996	$-98^*(7^{46}*(5-4^{43^2})+1)$
-31195119	$(9+8)^*(7*(-6+5)^4*(4^{43^2+1}))$	-32080823	$9^*(8-(7+6+5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-31195238	$(-9-8)^*(7*(6-5+4^{43^2})-1)$	-32080825	$9^*(8-(7+6+5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-31195272	$(-9-8)^*(7*(6-5+4^{43^2})+1)$	-32080967	$-9^*(8+(7+6+5^{4*3})^2)+1$
-31196428	$(-9-8)^*(7*(6+5+4^{43^2})-1)$	-32080969	$-9^*(8+(7+6+5^{4*3})^2)-1$
-31196462	$(-9-8)^*(7*(6+5+4^{43^2})+1)$	-32120463	$(-9-8)^*(7*(6^{45}+4^{43^2})-1)$
-31198689	$(-9-8)^*(7*(6^5+4^{43^2})-1)$	-32120497	$(-9-8)^*(7*(6^{45}+4^{43^2})+1)$
-31198723	$(-9-8)^*(7*(6^5+4^{43^2})+1)$	-32226645	$-9^*(8+7/6)^*(5^{44}*(3/2)+1)$
-31203323	$9^*(8-(7+6-5^{4*3})^2)+1$	-32235817	$9-8^*7^{46}*(5/4+3^2+1)$
-31203325	$9^*(8-(7+6-5^{4*3})^2)-1$	-32649624	$9^*(8-(7^{46}-5^{44})^*(32-1))$
-31203467	$-9^*(8+(7+6-5^{4*3})^2)+1$	-32649768	$-9^*(8+(7^{46}-5^{44})^*(32-1))$
-31203469	$-9^*(8+(7+6-5^{4*3})^2)-1$	-32798528	$-9^*(8-7^6-5^{4*3})^2+1$
-31224327	$9-8^*(7^{46+5^{44}})^*(32+1)$	-32798530	$-9^*(8-7^6-5^{4*3})^2-1$
-31224345	$-9-8^*(7^{46+5^{44}})^*(32+1)$	-32808933	$9^*(8-(7^{46}-54)^*(32-1))$
-31294536	$-98^*(7^{46}*(5/(4+3)+2)-1)$	-32809077	$-9^*(8+(7^{46}-54)^*(32-1))$
-31294617	$9-8^*(7^{46}*(5/4+32)-1)$	-32811744	$-9^*(8+76)^*((5^{44}/3)^2-1)$
-31295970	$-9^{(8-8+7+6)^*(5^4+3)^2+1}$	-32812407	$9-(8+76)^*(5^{44}*(3/2)-1)$
-31307447	$9^{48-7^{46}}*(5^{44+3+2}+1)$	-32812425	$-9-(8+76)^*(5^{44}*(3/2)-1)$
-31361790	$9^*(8-7^{46}*(5^{44}-3)/21)$	-32812575	$9-(8+76)^*(5^{44}*(3/2)+1)$
-31361934	$-9^*(8+7^{46}*(5^{44}-3)/21)$	-32812593	$-9-(8+76)^*(5^{44}*(3/2)+1)$
-31437657	$9^*(87-(6-5^{4*3})^2)+1$	-32813256	$-9^*(8+76)^*((5^{44}/3)^2+1)$
-31437675	$9^*(87-(6-5^{4*3})^2)-1$	-32818419	$9^*(8-(7^{46}-5^4)^*(32-1))$
-31437944	$9^*(8^*7-(6-5^{4*3})^2)+1$	-32818563	$-9^*(8+(7^{46}-5^4)^*(32-1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-32821033	$(98 - 7^6 * (5+4)) * (32-1)$	-33898401	$9 * (8 - (7^6+54) * 32-1)$
-32821632	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-5-4) * (32-1))$	-33898527	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+54) * 32-1)$
-32823814	$9 + (8 - 7^6 * (5+4)) * (32-1)$	-33898545	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+54) * 32+1)$
-32823864	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-5+4) * (32-1))$	-33904584	$-9 * 8 * ((7^6-5) * 4+321)$
-32823973	$98 - 7^6 * (5+4) * (32-1)$	-33979668	$9 * (87 * (6 - (5^4/3)^2)+1)$
-32824169	$-98 - 7^6 * (5+4) * (32-1)$	-33979686	$9 * (87 * (6 - (5^4/3)^2) - 1)$
-32824310	$9 - (8 + 7^6 * (5+4)) * (32-1)$	-33983757	$9 + 87 * (6 - 5^4 * (3/2) + 1)$
-32824422	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5-4) * (32-1))$	-33983775	$-9 + 87 * (6 - 5^4 * (3/2) + 1)$
-32826654	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5+4) * (32-1))$	-33983931	$9 + 87 * (6 - 5^4 * (3/2) - 1)$
-32827109	$(98 + 7^6 * (5+4)) * (-32+1)$	-33983949	$-9 + 87 * (6 - 5^4 * (3/2) - 1)$
-32829579	$9 * (8 - (7^6+5^4) * (32-1))$	-33984801	$9 - 87 * (6 + 5^4 * (3/2) - 1)$
-32829723	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5^4) * (32-1))$	-33984819	$-9 - 87 * (6 + 5^4 * (3/2) - 1)$
-32839065	$9 * (8 - (7^6+54) * (32-1))$	-33984975	$9 - 87 * (6 + 5^4 * (3/2) + 1)$
-32839209	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+54) * (32-1))$	-33989064	$9 * (-87 * (6 + (5^4/3)^2) + 1)$
-32998374	$9 * (8 - (7^6+5^4) * (32-1))$	-34000510	$(-9 - 8) * (7^6 * (5^4 - 3) - 2 - 1)$
-32998518	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5^4) * (32-1))$	-34000612	$(9 + 8) * (7^6 * (-5 - 4^3) - 2 - 1)$
-33029873	$-9 * (8^7 - 6 * (5 - 4^3)^2) + 1$	-34062831	$9 * (8 - (7^6+5^4) * 32+1)$
-33029875	$-9 * (8^7 - 6 * (5 - 4^3)^2) - 1$	-34062849	$9 * (8 - (7^6+5^4) * 32-1)$
-33030413	$-9 * (8^7 + 6 * (5 + 4^3)^2) + 1$	-34062975	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5^4) * 32-1)$
-33030415	$-9 * (8^7 + 6 * (5 + 4^3)^2) - 1$	-34062993	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5^4) * 32+1)$
-33073928	$9 * (8 - (7^6+5^4 * 3)^2) + 1$	-34164000	$-9 * (8/7 + 6) * (((5+4)^3)^2 - 1)$
-33073930	$9 * (8 - (7^6+5^4 * 3)^2) - 1$	-34257528	$9 * (8 - (76+5^4 * 3)^2 + 1)$
-33074072	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5^4 * 3)^2) + 1$	-34257546	$9 * (8 - (76+5^4 * 3)^2 - 1)$
-33074074	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5^4 * 3)^2) - 1$	-34257672	$-9 * (8 + (76+5^4 * 3)^2 - 1)$
-33202989	$(9+8) * (7 - (6-5+4)^3)^2 + 1$	-34257690	$-9 * (8 + (76+5^4 * 3)^2 + 1)$
-33203023	$(9+8) * (7 - (6-5+4)^3)^2 - 1$	-34402998	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 - 21)$
-33203227	$(-9-8) * (7 + (6-5+4)^3)^2 - 1$	-34404762	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 - 2 - 1)$
-33203261	$(-9-8) * (7 + (6-5+4)^3)^2 + 1$	-34404958	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 - 2 + 1)$
-33702831	$9 * (8 - (7^6-5^4) * 32+1)$	-34405007	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33702849	$9 * (8 - (7^6-5^4) * 32-1)$	-34405105	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33702975	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-5^4) * 32-1)$	-34405154	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 + 2 - 1)$
-33702993	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-5^4) * 32+1)$	-34405350	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 + 2 + 1)$
-33765165	$98 - 7^6 * ((5+4) * 32-1)$	-34407114	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 + 21)$
-33765361	$-98 - 7^6 * ((5+4) * 32-1)$	-34572636	$-98 * ((7^6-54) * 3 - 2 - 1)$
-33858360	$-9 * 8 * ((7^6-5) * 4 - 321)$	-34572832	$-98 * ((7^6-54) * 3 - 2 + 1)$
-33861240	$-9 * 8 * ((7^6+5) * 4 - 321)$	-34572881	$-98 * ((7^6-54) * 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33867279	$9 * (8 - (7^6-54) * 32+1)$	-34572979	$-98 * ((7^6-54) * 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33867297	$9 * (8 - (7^6-54) * 32-1)$	-34573028	$-98 * ((7^6-54) * 3 + 2 - 1)$
-33867423	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-54) * 32-1)$	-34573224	$-98 * ((7^6-54) * 3 + 2 + 1)$
-33867441	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-54) * 32+1)$	-34582828	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 - 2 + 1)$
-33877215	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-5^4) * 32-1)$	-34582877	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33877233	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-5^4) * 32+1)$	-34582975	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33878583	$-9 * (8 * (7^6-5) * 4 - 321)$	-34583024	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 + 2 - 1)$
-33879843	$-9 * (8 * (7^6+5) * 4 - 321)$	-34583220	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 + 2 + 1)$
-33880203	$-9 * (8 * (7^6+5) * 4 - 321)$	-34584102	$-98 * ((7^6-5-4) * 3 - 21)$
-33880383	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-5-4) * 32-1)$	-34584984	$-98 * ((7^6-5^4) * 3 + 21)$
-33880401	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-5-4) * 32+1)$	-34586111	$-98 * ((7^6-5-4) * 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33881039	$9 * 8 * ((7^6-5) * 4 + 3^2) + 1$	-34586209	$-98 * ((7^6-5-4) * 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33881041	$9 * 8 * ((7^6-5) * 4 + 3^2) - 1$	-34587238	$-98 * ((7^6-5) * (4 - 3 + 2) - 1)$
-33881175	$-9 * (8 * (7^6-5) * 4 - 32-1)$	-34587434	$-98 * ((7^6-5) * (4 - 3 + 2) + 1)$
-33881417	$-9 * (8 * (7^6-5) * 4 - 3^2) + 1$	-34588320	$(-98 * 7^6 + 54 * 3) * (2+1)$
-33881419	$-9 * (8 * (7^6-5) * 4 - 3^2) - 1$	-34588463	$-98 * ((7^6-5+4) * 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33881525	$-9 * (8 * (7^6-5) * 4 + 3^2) + 1$	-34588561	$-98 * ((7^6-5+4) * 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33881527	$-9 * (8 * (7^6-5) * 4 + 3^2) - 1$	-34588860	$(-98 * 7^6 - 54/3) * (2+1)$
-33881903	$9 * 8 * ((7^6-5) * 4 - 3^2) + 1$	-34589051	$-98 * ((7^6+5-4) * 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33881905	$9 * 8 * ((7^6-5) * 4 - 3^2) - 1$	-34589149	$-98 * ((7^6+5-4) * 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33883263	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5-4) * 32-1)$	-34589292	$(-98 * 7^6 - 54 * 3) * (2+1)$
-33883281	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5-4) * 32+1)$	-34590178	$-98 * ((7^6+5) * (4 - 3 + 2) - 1)$
-33883353	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5/4) * 32+1)$	-34590374	$-98 * ((7^6+5) * (4 - 3 + 2) + 1)$
-33883919	$9 * 8 * ((7^6+5) * 4 + 3^2) + 1$	-34591403	$-98 * ((7^6+5+4) * 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33883921	$9 * 8 * ((7^6+5) * 4 + 3^2) - 1$	-34591501	$-98 * ((7^6+5+4) * 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33884297	$-9 * (8 * (7^6+5) * 4 - 3^2) + 1$	-34592628	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3 - 21)$
-33884299	$-9 * (8 * (7^6+5) * 4 - 3^2) - 1$	-34593510	$-98 * ((7^6+5+4) * 3 + 21)$
-33884405	$-9 * (8 * (7^6+5) * 4 + 3^2) + 1$	-34594392	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3 - 2 - 1)$
-33884407	$-9 * (8 * (7^6+5) * 4 + 3^2) - 1$	-34594588	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3 - 2 + 1)$
-33884783	$9 * 8 * ((7^6+5) * 4 - 3^2) + 1$	-34594637	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33884785	$9 * 8 * ((7^6+5) * 4 - 3^2) - 1$	-34594735	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33885981	$-9 * (8 * (7^6+5) * 4 + 321)$	-34594784	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3 + 2 - 1)$
-33887241	$-9 * (8 * (7^6+5) * 4 + 321)$	-34604388	$-98 * ((7^6+54) * 3 - 2 - 1)$
-33888735	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5^4) * 32-1)$	-34604584	$-98 * ((7^6+54) * 3 - 2 + 1)$
-33888753	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5^4) * 32+1)$	-34604633	$-98 * ((7^6+54) * 3 - 2^{\wedge} - 1)$
-33898383	$9 * (8 - (7^6+54) * 32+1)$	-34604731	$-98 * ((7^6+54) * 3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-34604780	$-98 * ((7^6+54) * 3+2-1)$	-35969280	$9 * -87 * ((6+5^4/3)^2-1)$
-34604976	$-98 * ((7^6+54) * 3+2+1)$	-35970054	$-9 * (87 * (6+5^4/3)^2-1)$
-34700673	$(-98+7^6*5) * (4-3*21)$	-35970072	$-9 * (87 * (6+5^4/3)^2+1)$
-34705974	$9 - (8-7^6*5) * (4-3*21)$	-35970846	$9 * -87 * ((6+5^4/3)^2+1)$
-34706357	$98+7^6*5 * (4-3*21)$	-35984070	$(9+8) * (7^6-54) * (3-21)$
-34706553	$-98+7^6*5 * (4-3*21)$	-35999082	$-9 * 8 * (7^6 * (5/4+3) - 21)$
-34706918	$9 + (8+7^6*5) * (4-3*21)$	-36000237	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * 54/3 - 21)$
-34706936	$-9 + (8+7^6*5) * (4-3*21)$	-36000475	$(-9-8) * ((7^6 * (5+4) - 3) * 2-1)$
-34712237	$(98+7^6*5) * (4-3*21)$	-36000509	$(-9-8) * ((7^6 * (5+4) - 3) * 2+1)$
-34756056	$9 * (8 - (7^6-5^4) * (32+1))$	-36000575	$-9 * (8 * 7^6 * (5/4+3) - 2) + 1$
-34756200	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-5^4) * (32+1))$	-36000613	$-9 * (8 * 7^6 * (5/4+3) + 2) - 1$
-34770498	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3-21)$	-36000679	$(-9-8) * ((7^6 * (5+4) + 3) * 2-1)$
-34772262	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3-2-1)$	-36000713	$(-9-8) * ((7^6 * (5+4) + 3) * 2+1)$
-34772458	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3-2+1)$	-36000951	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * 54/3 + 21)$
-34772507	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-36002106	$-9 * 8 * (7^6 * (5/4+3) + 21)$
-34772605	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-36017118	$(9+8) * (7^6+54) * (3-21)$
-34772654	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3+2-1)$	-36096063	$-9 * (8 * (7^6+5^4/3))^2+1$
-34772850	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3+2+1)$	-36096065	$-9 * (8 * (7^6+5^4/3))^2-1$
-34774614	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4) * 3+21)$	-36175734	$(9 * 8 - 7 * 6 * 5) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-34857207	$-9 * ((87+6+5^4 * 3))^2-1$	-36176010	$(9 * 8 - 7 * 6 * 5) * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-34857225	$-9 * ((87+6+5^4 * 3))^2+1$	-36235883	$9+8 * 7^6 * (5-43-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-34925643	$9 * (8 - (7^6-54) * (32+1))$	-36328023	$9 - (87+6) * (5^4 * (3/2) - 1)$
-34925787	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-54) * (32+1))$	-36328041	$-9 - (87+6) * (5^4 * (3/2) - 1)$
-34935741	$9 * (8 - (7^6-5 * 4) * (32+1))$	-36328209	$9 - (87+6) * (5^4 * (3/2) + 1)$
-34935885	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-5 * 4) * (32+1))$	-36328227	$-9 - (87+6) * (5^4 * (3/2) + 1)$
-34938519	$(98-7^6 * (5+4)) * (32+1)$	-36353443	$98-7^6 * (5 * (4^{\wedge}3-2) - 1)$
-34939008	$9 * (8 - (7^6-5-4) * (32+1))$	-36353469	$9 * 8 - 7^6 * (5 * (4^{\wedge}3-2) - 1)$
-34939152	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-5-4) * (32+1))$	-36353613	$9 * -8 - 7^6 * (5 * (4^{\wedge}3-2) - 1)$
-34941480	$9 + (8-7^6 * (5+4)) * (32+1)$	-36353639	$-98-7^6 * (5 * (4^{\wedge}3-2) - 1)$
-34941498	$-9 + (8-7^6 * (5+4)) * (32+1)$	-36391615	$(9 * 8 - 7) * (-6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3) * 2+1)$
-34941528	$-9 * (8 + (7^6-5+4) * (32+1))$	-36391745	$(9 * 8 - 7) * (-6^{\wedge}(-5+4 * 3) * 2-1)$
-34941655	$98-7^6 * (5+4) * (32+1)$	-36529936	$(-9 / ((8-7 * (6^{\wedge}5-4)) / 3))^2)^{\wedge}-1$
-34941851	$-98-7^6 * (5+4) * (32+1)$	-36531552	$9-87 * ((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^2-1)$
-34942008	$9 - (8+7^6 * (5+4)) * (32+1)$	-36531570	$-9-87 * ((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^2-1)$
-34942026	$-9 - (8+7^6 * (5+4)) * (32+1)$	-36531726	$9-87 * ((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^2+1)$
-34942122	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5-4) * (32+1))$	-36531744	$-9-87 * ((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^2+1)$
-34944498	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5+4) * (32+1))$	-36543013	$(9+8) * (7+6/5) * (-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-34944987	$(98+7^6 * (5+4)) * (-32-1)$	-36626704	$(-9 / ((8+7 * (6^{\wedge}5+4)) / 3))^2)^{\wedge}-1$
-34947621	$9 * (8 - (7^6+5 * 4) * (32+1))$	-36706293	$-9 * (8 * 7^6-5) * (4/3+2+1)$
-34947765	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5 * 4) * (32+1))$	-36824039	$98-7^6 * ((5^4+3) / 2-1)$
-34957719	$9 * (8 - (7^6+54) * (32+1))$	-36824065	$9 * 8 - 7^6 * ((5^4+3) / 2-1)$
-34957863	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+54) * (32+1))$	-36824209	$-9 * 8 - 7^6 * ((5^4+3) / 2-1)$
-35127306	$9 * (8 - (7^6+5^4) * (32+1))$	-36824235	$-98-7^6 * ((5^4+3) / 2-1)$
-35127450	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5^4) * (32+1))$	-36885942	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6) * (5^4-3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-35156385	$-9 * (8+7) * (6 * (5^4/3))^2+1$	-36897178	$9^{\wedge}8 / (-7/6) - 5 / ((4/3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-35176953	$98-7^6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-36897192	$9^{\wedge}8 / (7/-6) - (5+4) / (3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-35177149	$-98-7^6 * (5 * 4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-36903438	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6) * (5^4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-35247968	$-9 * (8 * (7+6) + 5^4 * 3))^2+1$	-36907812	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6) * (5^4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-35247970	$-9 * (8 * (7+6) + 5^4 * 3))^2-1$	-36925308	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6) * (5^4+3^{\wedge}(-2+1))$
-35296200	$9 * 8 * (7^6+5) * (-4 - (3 * 2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-37001214	$9 * (8 - (7^6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3)) * 21)$
-35311302	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6) * (5^4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-37001358	$-9 * (8 + (7^6+5^{\wedge}4(4+3)) * 21)$
-35380656	$9 * ((8+7) * (65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-37057125	$(98 - (7^6 * 5-4) * 3) * 21$
-35380674	$9 * ((8+7) * (65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-37057629	$(98 - (7^6 * 5+4) * 3) * 21$
-35412332	$9+8+7^6 * (5 * 4-321)$	-37058670	$9 + (8-7^6 * 5+4) * 3 * 21$
-35412348	$9-8+7^6 * (5 * 4-321)$	-37058742	$9 * ((8-7^6 * 5) * (4+3) + 21)$
-35412350	$-9+8+7^6 * (5 * 4-321)$	-37058912	$9 * ((8-7^6 * 5) * (4+3) + 2) + 1$
-35412366	$-9-8+7^6 * (5 * 4-321)$	-37058914	$9 * ((8-7^6 * 5) * (4+3) + 2) - 1$
-35643376	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^6 * 543) / (-2-1)$	-37058948	$9 * ((8-7^6 * 5) * (4+3) - 2) + 1$
-35765224	$9 * 8 - 7^6 * (5^4-321)$	-37058950	$9 * ((8-7^6 * 5) * (4+3) - 2) - 1$
-35765283	$9+8 * (7^6 * (5-43) + 2^{\wedge}-1)$	-37059006	$9 + (8 - (7^6 * 5-4) * 3) * 21$
-35765291	$9+8 * (7^6 * (5-43) - 2^{\wedge}-1)$	-37059085	$98 - (7^6 * 5-4) * 3 * 21$
-35765301	$-9+8 * (7^6 * (5-43) + 2^{\wedge}-1)$	-37059174	$9 + (8-7^6 * 5-4) * 3 * 21$
-35765309	$-9+8 * (7^6 * (5-43) - 2^{\wedge}-1)$	-37059281	$-98 - (7^6 * 5-4) * 3 * 21$
-35765368	$-9 * 8 - 7^6 * (5^4-321)$	-37059318	$-9 * (8+7^6 * 5 * (4+3) - 21)$
-35861364	$9 * (8-76/5 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-37059337	$98-7^6 * 5 * (4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
-35861508	$-9 * (8+76/5 * (4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-37059533	$-98-7^6 * 5 * (4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
-35871630	$(9^{\wedge}8-765) * (-4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-37059589	$98 - (7^6 * 5+4) * 3 * 21$
-35872905	$(9^{\wedge}8+765) * (-4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-37059678	$9 - (8+7^6 * 5-4) * 3 * 21$
-35882847	$98-7^6 * 5 * (4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	-37059785	$-98 - (7^6 * 5+4) * 3 * 21$
-35882873	$9 * 8 - 7^6 * 5 * (4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	-37059846	$9 - (8 + (7^6 * 5+4) * 3) * 21$
-35883017	$9 * -8 - 7^6 * 5 * (4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	-37059920	$-9 * ((8+7^6 * 5) * (4+3) - 2) + 1$
-35883043	$-98-7^6 * 5 * (4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	-37059922	$-9 * ((8+7^6 * 5) * (4+3) - 2) - 1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-37059956	$-9 * ((8+7^6 * 5) * (4+3)+2)+1$	-38587231	$9-8 * ((7^6-5) * (43-2)+1)$
-37059958	$-9 * ((8+7^6 * 5) * (4+3)+2)-1$	-38590495	$9-8 * ((7^6+5) * (43-2)-1)$
-37060182	$9-(8+7^6 * 5+4) * 3 * 21$	-38590511	$9-8 * ((7^6+5) * (43-2)+1)$
-37060200	$-9-(8+7^6 * 5+4) * 3 * 21$	-38706423	$98-7^6 * (5 * (4^3+2)-1)$
-37061241	$(98+(7^6 * 5-4) * 3) * -21$	-38706449	$9 * 8-7^6 * (5 * (4^3+2)-1)$
-37061745	$(98+(7^6 * 5+4) * 3) * -21$	-38706593	$9 * -8-7^6 * (5 * (4^3+2)-1)$
-37109280	$(9-8 * (7+6)) * (5^4 * (3/2)-1)$	-38706619	$-98-7^6 * (5 * (4^3+2)-1)$
-37109470	$(9-8 * (7+6)) * (5^4 * (3/2)+1)$	-38941721	$98-7^6 * (5 * (4^3+2)+1)$
-37219126	$-98 * (7^6-5+4^3 * 2-1)$	-38941747	$9 * 8-7^6 * (5 * (4^3+2)+1)$
-37219322	$-98 * (7^6-5+4^3 * 2+1)$	-38941891	$9 * -8-7^6 * (5 * (4^3+2)+1)$
-37220106	$-98 * (7^6+5+4^3 * 2-1)$	-38941917	$-98-7^6 * (5 * (4^3+2)+1)$
-37220302	$-98 * (7^6+5+4^3 * 2+1)$	-39304072	$-9 * 8-(7^6 * (-6+5+4)-3)^(2+1)$
-37294635	$98-7^6 * (5 * 4^3-2-1)$	-39412317	$98-7^6 * 5 * (4+3 * 21)$
-37294661	$98-7^6 * (5 * 4^3-2-1)$	-39412487	$9 * -8-7^6 * 5 * (4^3+2+1)$
-37294805	$9 * -8-7^6 * (5 * 4^3-2-1)$	-39412513	$-98-7^6 * 5 * (4+3 * 21)$
-37294831	$-98-7^6 * (5 * 4^3-2-1)$	-39528375	$9-8 * (7^6-5) * (43-2+1)$
-37529933	$98-7^6 * (5 * 4^3-2+1)$	-39531735	$9-8 * (7^6+5) * (43-2+1)$
-37529959	$98-7^6 * (5 * 4^3-2+1)$	-39845727	$9-(87+65) * (4^3 * 2-1)$
-37530103	$-9 * 8-7^6 * (5/4^3-2+1)$	-39845745	$-9-(87+65) * (4^3 * 2-1)$
-37530129	$-98-7^6 * (5 * 4^3-2+1)$	-39846031	$9-(87+65) * (4^3 * 2+1)$
-37645990	$(9-8 * (7^6-5) * 4) * (3^2+1)$	-39846049	$-9-(87+65) * (4^3 * 2+1)$
-37646170	$(-9-8 * (7^6-5) * 4) * (3^2+1)$	-39995203	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * 5 * 4-3 * 21)$
-37647496	$(-9-8 * (7^6 * 5-4)) * (3^2-1)$	-39998943	$(-9-8) * ((7^6-5) * 4 * (3+2)-1)$
-37647561	$98-7^6 * 5 * 4^3+21$	-39998951	$9-8 * (7^6-5) * (43-2^2-1)$
-37647570	$(9+(8/7^6-6-5) * 4) * (-3^2-1)$	-39998977	$(-9-8) * ((7^6-5) * 4 * (3+2)+1)$
-37647650	$(-9-8 * (7^6 * 5^4-3)) * 2/1$	-40000201	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * 5^4-3^2+1)$
-37647710	$(9-8 * (7^6 * 5^4+3)) * 2/1$	-40000524	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5^4+3^2-1)$
-37647799	$-98-7^6 * 5 * 4^3-21$	-40000541	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * 5^4-3^2-1)$
-37647864	$(9-8 * (7^6 * 5+4)) * (3^2-1)$	-40000557	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * 5^4-3^2+1)$
-37647970	$(9+(8/7^6-6+5) * 4) * (-3^2-1)$	-40000763	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * 5^4+3^2-1)$
-37649190	$(9-8 * (7^6+5) * 4) * (3^2+1)$	-40000779	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * 5^4+3^2+1)$
-37649370	$(-9-8 * (7^6+5) * 4) * (3^2+1)$	-40000796	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * 5^4+3^2-1)$
-37665838	$((9^8-7)/-6-5)/4+3) * 21$	-40001119	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * 5^4+3^2+1)$
-37665964	$((9^8-7)/-6-5)/4-3) * 21$	-40002343	$(-9-8) * ((7^6+5) * 4 * (3+2)-1)$
-37745847	$-9 * (8^6 * (7+6-5)/4-3 * 21)$	-40002351	$9-8 * (7^6+5) * (43-2^2-1)$
-37751625	$-9 * (8^6 * (7+6-5)/4+3 * 21)$	-40002377	$(-9-8) * ((7^6+5) * 4 * (3+2)+1)$
-37758892	$9+8-(7^6-5 * 4) * 3 * 21$	-40006117	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * 5^4+3 * 21)$
-37758908	$9-8-(7^6-5 * 4) * 3 * 21$	-40235697	$9 * (8+7^6 * (5-4 * 3)+21)$
-37758910	$-9+8-(7^6-5 * 4) * 3 * 21$	-40235859	$9 * (8+7^6 * (5-4 * 3)+2+1)$
-37758926	$-9-8-(7^6-5 * 4) * 3 * 21$	-40235865	$9 * (8+7^6 * (5-4 * 3))+21$
-37771732	$9+8-(7^6+5 * 4) * 3 * 21$	-40235907	$9 * (8+7^6 * (5-4 * 3))-21$
-37771748	$9-8-(7^6+5 * 4) * 3 * 21$	-40236003	$9 * (-8+7^6 * (5-4 * 3)+2+1)$
-37771750	$-9+8-(7^6+5 * 4) * 3 * 21$	-40236009	$9 * (-8+7^6 * (5-4 * 3))+21$
-37771766	$-9-8-(7^6+5 * 4) * 3 * 21$	-40236021	$9 * (-8+7^6 * (5-4 * 3)+2-1)$
-37968993	$9^8 * ((8+7)/6) * (-5^4 * (4+3)) * 2-1$	-40236039	$9 * (-8+7^6 * (5-4 * 3))-2+1$
-38000529	$98-7^6 * (54 * 3^2-1)$	-40236051	$9 * (-8+7^6 * (5-4 * 3))-21$
-38118123	$9 * ((8-7^6 * 54/3) * 2+1)$	-40236057	$9 * (-8+7^6 * (5-4 * 3))-2-1$
-38118141	$9 * ((8-7^6 * 54/3) * 2-1)$	-40236075	$9 * (8+7^6 * (5-4 * 3))-21$
-38235827	$98-7^6 * (54 * 3^2+1)$	-40236219	$9 * (-8+7^6 * (5-4 * 3))-21$
-38236023	$-98-7^6 * (54 * 3^2+1)$	-40310279	$9 * 8 * (7-6^6 * (-5+4 * 3) * 2)+1$
-38258649	$9^8 * ((8+7)/6) * (-54^3+21)$	-40310281	$9 * 8 * (7-6^6 * (-5+4 * 3) * 2)-1$
-38260104	$(9^8-76 * 54) * (3^2-1)$	-40311287	$9 * 8 * (7-6^6 * (-5+4 * 3) * 2)+1$
-38261032	$(9^8-765 * 4) * (3^2-1)$	-40311289	$9 * 8 * (7-6^6 * (-5+4 * 3) * 2)-1$
-38263582	$(9^8-765/4) * (3^2-1)$	-40335085	$-98 * (7^6-54) * (3+2^2-1)$
-38263922	$(9^8+765/4) * (3^2-1)$	-40353418	$(-98 * 7^6+54) * (3+2^2-1)$
-38266472	$(9^8+765 * 4) * (3^2-1)$	-40353796	$(-98 * 7^6-54) * (3+2^2-1)$
-38267400	$(9^8+76 * 54) * (3^2-1)$	-40370162	$-98/(7/((6+5) * 4^3 * 2-1))$
-38268855	$9^8 * ((8+7)/6) * (-54^3-21)$	-40370190	$-98/(7/((6+5) * 4^3 * 2+1))$
-38277036	$98 * (7^6-5^4 * (3/2)+1)$	-40372129	$-98 * (7^6+54) * (3+2^2-1)$
-38277232	$98 * (7^6-5^4 * (3/2)-1)$	-40469503	$9-8 * ((7^6-5) * 43-2-1)$
-38279878	$98 * (7+6-5^4 * (3/2)+1)$	-40469519	$9-8 * ((7^6-5) * 43-2+1)$
-38280074	$98 * (7+6-5^4 * (3/2)-1)$	-40469523	$9-8 * ((7^6-5) * 43-2^2-1)$
-38281054	$98 * (7-6-5^4 * (3/2)+1)$	-40469531	$9-8 * ((7^6-5) * 43+2^2-1)$
-38281446	$-98 * (7-6+5^4 * (3/2)+1)$	-40469535	$9-8 * ((7^6-5) * 43+2-1)$
-38282426	$-98 * (7+6+5^4 * (3/2)-1)$	-40469549	$-9-8 * ((7^6-5) * 43+2^2-1)$
-38282622	$-98 * (7+6+5^4 * (3/2)+1)$	-40469551	$9-8 * ((7^6-5) * 43+2+1)$
-38285268	$-98 * (7^6+5^4 * (3/2)-1)$	-40469569	$-9-8 * ((7^6-5) * 43+2+1)$
-38285464	$-98 * (7^6+5^4 * (3/2)+1)$	-40472943	$9-8 * ((7^6+5) * 43-2-1)$
-38371606	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4 * (4+3)) * 2-1)$	-40472959	$9-8 * ((7^6+5) * 43-2+1)$
-38371802	$-98 * ((7^6+5^4 * (4+3)) * 2+1)$	-40472963	$9-8 * ((7^6+5) * 43-2^2-1)$
-38499948	$-9^8 * (-8+7+6) * (5^4+3^2+1)$	-40472971	$9-8 * ((7^6+5) * 43+2^2-1)$
-38587215	$9-8 * ((7^6-5) * (43-2)-1)$	-40472975	$9-8 * ((7^6+5) * 43+2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-40472991	$9 \cdot 8^*((7^6+5)^{43+2+1})$	-42350523	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 43) + 21$
-40781095	$9 \cdot 8/76^*((5+4)^{43^2-1})$	-42350565	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 43) - 21$
-40894308	$(-98+7-65)^*(4^3 \cdot 2-1)$	-42350733	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 43) + 21)$
-40894620	$(-98+7-65)^*(4^3 \cdot 2+1)$	-42351823	$9 \cdot 8^*((7^6-5)^*(43+2) - 1)$
-40940103	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6-5)^*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-42351857	$-9 \cdot 8^*((7^6-5)^*(43+2)+1)$
-40940121	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6-5)^*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-42351876	$(-98+7^6 \cdot 5^4)^*(3-21)$
-40943583	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6+5)^*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-42351911	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) + 1$
-41072314	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^*((4^3)^2-1)$	-42351913	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) - 1$
-41149808	$98^*(7 - (6^5/4/3)^2+1)$	-42352083	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 43/2) - 1)$
-41150004	$98^*(7 - (6^5/4/3)^2-1)$	-42352199	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot (3+2)) + 1$
-41151180	$-98^*(7 + (6^5/4/3)^2-1)$	-42352201	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot (3+2)) - 1$
-41151376	$-98^*(7 + (6^5/4/3)^2+1)$	-42352343	$-9 \cdot (8/(7^{\wedge}-6/5) - (4^3)^2) + 1$
-41162445	$9/8^*(7^6 \cdot 5^4 - 3)/(-2-1)$	-42352345	$-9 \cdot (8/(7^{\wedge}-6/5) - (4^3)^2) - 1$
-41317047	$9 \cdot 8^* - 7 + (6^5)^{\wedge} 4 \cdot 321$	-42352608	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3/(2+1))$
-41410679	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6-5)^*(43+2-1)$	-42352631	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) + 1$
-41412659	$9 \cdot (8^*7^6+5)^*(43+2-1)$	-42352633	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) - 1$
-41414199	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6+5)^*(43+2-1)$	-42352757	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) + 2) + 1$
-41421638	$98 \cdot (7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-42352759	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) + 2) - 1$
-41421808	$-9 \cdot 8^* - (7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4)+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-42352793	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) - 2) + 1$
-41508178	$9 \cdot 8^*7/(6/543)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-42352795	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) - 2) - 1$
-41508196	$-9 \cdot 8^*7/(6/543)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-42352919	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) + 1$
-41511447	$9 \cdot 8^*((7+6)/(5+4)^{\wedge} 3 \cdot 2-1)$	-42352921	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) - 1$
-41542910	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^*(5^*(4^3)^2-1)$	-42353031	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4) + 321$
-41546439	$9 \cdot 8^*((-7^{\wedge}(-6+5)+4)^{\wedge}-3 \cdot 2-1)$	-42353232	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^6 \cdot 5 - 43) + 21$
-41778208	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^*(5^*(4^3)^2+1)$	-42353274	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^6 \cdot 5 - 43) - 21$
-41923938	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^6-5^4 \cdot 3) \cdot 21$	-42353283	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^6 \cdot 5 - 4) + 321$
-41980344	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^6-54-3) \cdot 21$	-42353299	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4) + 3^2) - 1$
-41982486	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^6-54+3) \cdot 21$	-42353981	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4) + 3^2) + 1$
-41983557	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^6-5-43) \cdot 21$	-42353997	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^6 \cdot 5 + 4) - 321$
-41987127	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^6+5-43) \cdot 21$	-42354048	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^6 \cdot 5 + 43) - 21$
-41994267	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^6-54/3) \cdot 21$	-42354249	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4) - 321$
-41998635	$(98 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^4 - 3) \cdot 21$	-42354359	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) + 1$
-42000516	$9 + (8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^4 - 3) \cdot 21$	-42354361	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) - 1$
-42000595	$98 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^4 - 3 \cdot 21$	-42354485	$9 \cdot (-8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3) + 2) + 1$
-42000791	$-98 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^4 - 3 \cdot 21$	-42354487	$9 \cdot (-8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3) + 2) - 1$
-42000852	$9 \cdot (8+7^6 \cdot 5^4 - 3) \cdot 21$	-42354521	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3) + 2) + 1$
-42002751	$(98+7^6 \cdot 5^4 - 3) \cdot 21$	-42354523	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3) + 2) - 1$
-42007119	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^6+54/3) \cdot 21$	-42354647	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) + 1$
-42007707	$(9 \cdot 8^*(7/(6/54))^{\wedge} 3) \cdot 21$	-42354649	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) - 1$
-42008085	$(-9 \cdot 8^*(7/(6/54))^{\wedge} 3) \cdot 21$	-42354935	$9 \cdot (-8/(7^{\wedge}-6/5) - (4^3)^2) + 1$
-42014259	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^6-5+43) \cdot 21$	-42354937	$9 \cdot (-8/(7^{\wedge}-6/5) - (4^3)^2) - 1$
-42017829	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^6+5+43) \cdot 21$	-42355079	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot (3+2)) + 1$
-42018900	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^6+54-3) \cdot 21$	-42355081	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot (3+2)) - 1$
-42021042	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^6+54+3) \cdot 21$	-42355367	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) + 1$
-42058527	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^6+54^3) \cdot 21$	-42355369	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) - 1$
-42077448	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^6+5^4 \cdot 3) \cdot 21$	-42355404	$(98+7^6 \cdot 5^4) \cdot (3-21)$
-42205023	$(-9 \cdot 87-65)^*(4^3 \cdot 2-1)$	-42355423	$9 \cdot 8^*((7^6+5)^*(43+2) - 1)$
-42205345	$(-9 \cdot 87-65)^*(4^3 \cdot 2+1)$	-42356061	$-9 \cdot ((8^*7^6+54)^*(3+2) - 1)$
-42220503	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) + 1)$	-42356493	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^6 \cdot 5 - 4 + 321)$
-42220521	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3 \cdot 2) - 1)$	-42356547	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 43) - 21)$
-42248804	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^*((4^3)^2+1)$	-42356709	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 43) - 2 - 1)$
-42260292	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6-5^4) \cdot 321$	-42356715	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 43) + 21$
-42316775	$9 \cdot (-8^*7^6 \cdot 5 + (4^3)^2) + 1$	-42356757	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 43) - 21$
-42316777	$9 \cdot (-8^*7^6 \cdot 5 + (4^3)^2) - 1$	-42356925	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 43) + 21)$
-42322464	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 432 - 1)$	-42358059	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3) - 21)$
-42322527	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 432) - 1)$	-42358437	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3) + 21)$
-42322545	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 432) + 1)$	-42361767	$-9 \cdot (8/7^{\wedge}-6 \cdot 5 + 4^3 \cdot 21)$
-42322608	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 432 + 1)$	-42364007	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 5 \cdot (4^3)^2) + 1$
-42330240	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4 - 321)$	-42364009	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 5 \cdot (4^3)^2) - 1$
-42330816	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4 - 321)$	-42365196	$-9 \cdot (8/7^{\wedge}-6 \cdot 5 + 4^3 \cdot 321)$
-42334191	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6-54)^*(3+2) - 1)$	-42365736	$-9 \cdot (8/7^{\wedge}-6 \cdot 5 + 4^3 \cdot 21)$
-42334272	$-9 \cdot 8^*((7^6-54)^*(3+2) + 1)$	-42370272	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$
-42336990	$9 \cdot (-8^*7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$	-42370290	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$
-42337008	$9 \cdot (-8^*7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$	-42376464	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4 + 321)$
-42343271	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 5 + (4^3)^2) + 1$	-42377040	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4 + 321)$
-42343273	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 5 + (4^3)^2) - 1$	-42384672	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$
-42348843	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3) - 21)$	-42384735	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3) - 1)$
-42349221	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4^3) + 21)$	-42384753	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3) + 1)$
-42349743	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^6 \cdot 5 - 432 - 1)$	-42384816	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 + 4^3 + 1)$
-42349761	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^6 \cdot 5 - 432 + 1)$	-42390503	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^6 \cdot 5 + (4^3)^2) + 1$
-42350355	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 43) - 21)$	-42390505	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^6 \cdot 5 + (4^3)^2) - 1$
-42350463	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^6 \cdot 5 - 4) - 321)$	-42467257	$9 \cdot (8 - (7+6+5)^4 \cdot 3^2) - 1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-42467399	$-9*(8+(7+6+5)*4^3)^2+1$	-44564310	$(-98-7-65)*(4^3)^2-1$
-42467401	$-9*(8+(7+6+5)*4^3)^2-1$	-44564650	$(-98-7-65)*(4^3)^2+1$
-42482745	$-9/8*(7^6-5-4)*321$	-44581995	$9^8*((-7-6)/(5+4)^3)^2-1$
-42485634	$-9/8*(7^6-5+4)*321$	-44706611	$9-8*7^6*(5+43-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-42486759	$-9*(8*(7^6*5+43)^2)-1$	-44818662	$(98-7^6*(5*4)^3)/21$
-42486777	$-9*(8*(7^6*5+43)^2)+1$	-44826623	$-9*(8^7+(6+5)*4^3)^2+1$
-42706587	$9*8*7^6*(-5-(4*3)^2)^{\wedge}-1$	-44826625	$-9*(8^7+(6+5)*4^3)^2-1$
-42922062	$9^8*(76/54*3)^2-1$	-44998758	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1))$
-43005168	$9^8*(76/54*3)^2-1$	-44998902	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1))$
-43171380	$9^8*(-76/(54*3)^2-1)$	-45002583	$9*(8-(7^6+5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1))$
-43292983	$9-8*(7^6-5)*(43+2+1)$	-45002727	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1))$
-43293001	$-9-8*(7^6-5)*(43+2+1)$	-45112438	$98*(7^6*5-4^{\wedge}(3^2+1))$
-43294593	$9-(8*7^6-5)*(43+2+1)$	-45177203	$9-8*(7^6*(5+43)-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-43295053	$9-(8*7^6+5)*(43+2+1)$	-45177229	$-9-8*(7^6*(5+43)+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-43296663	$9-8*(7^6+5)*(43+2+1)$	-45455943	$(9-876)/5*(4^3)^2+1$
-43348830	$(98-7^6/5)*(43^2+1)$	-45527967	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*43+21)$
-43410699	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*(43-2)-1)$	-45528111	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*43-21)$
-43410717	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*(43-2)+1)$	-45528135	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*43)+21$
-43414389	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*(43-2)-1)$	-45528177	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*43)-21$
-43414407	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*(43-2)+1)$	-45528273	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*43-2-1)$
-43515321	$9+(8-7^6/5)*(43^2+1)$	-45528279	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*43)+21$
-43515339	$-9+(8-7^6/5)*(43^2+1)$	-45528291	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*43+2+1)$
-43530032	$98-7^6/5*(43^2+1)$	-45528309	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*43+2-1)$
-43530228	$-98-7^6/5*(43^2+1)$	-45528321	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*43)-21$
-43544921	$9-(8+7^6/5)*(43^2+1)$	-45528327	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*43+2+1)$
-43544939	$9-(8+7^6/5)*(43^2+1)$	-45528345	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*43-21)$
-43568499	$(9-876/5)*(4^3)^2+1$	-45528489	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*43+21)$
-43711430	$(-98-7^6/5)*(43^2+1)$	-45531837	$9*(8-(7^6+5)*43+21)$
-43803933	$9-(8^7-6*5^4*3)*21$	-45531981	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*43-21)$
-43803951	$9-(8^7-6*5^4*3)*21$	-45532005	$9*(8-(7^6+5)*43)+21$
-44000682	$9-(8^7-6-5^4*3)*21$	-45532047	$9*(8-(7^6+5)*43)-21$
-44000700	$-9-(8^7-6-5^4*3)*21$	-45532143	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*43-2-1)$
-44000709	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(54-32))-1$	-45532149	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*43)+21$
-44000743	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(54-32)+1)$	-45532161	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*43-2+1)$
-44000934	$9-(8^7+6-5^4*3)*21$	-45532179	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*43+2-1)$
-44000952	$-9-(8^7+6-5^4*3)*21$	-45532191	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*43)-21$
-44013933	$9-(8^7-6*5^4/3)*21$	-45532197	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*43+2+1)$
-44013951	$-9-(8^7-6*5^4/3)*21$	-45532215	$9*(8-(7^6+5)*43-21)$
-44035682	$9-(8^7-6-5^4/3)*21$	-45532359	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*43+21)$
-44035700	$-9-(8^7-6-5^4/3)*21$	-45612882	$(9+(8+7)*(6+5))*(-4^3)^2+1$
-44035934	$9-(8^7+6-5^4/3)*21$	-45647803	$9-8*7^6*(5+43+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-44035952	$-9-(8^7+6-5^4/3)*21$	-45927795	$9-876/5*(4^3)^2+1$
-44044432	$9-(8^7-6+5^4/3)*21$	-45927813	$-9-876/5*(4^3)^2+1$
-44044450	$-9-(8^7-6+5^4/3)*21$	-46000708	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5*4+3))-2-1$
-44044684	$9-(8^7+6+5^4/3)*21$	-46000742	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5*4+3))-2+1$
-44044702	$-9-(8^7+6+5^4/3)*21$	-46000810	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5*4+3)+2+1)$
-44066433	$9-(8^7+6*5^4/3)*21$	-46006263	$-9*((87/6+5)*4^3)^2-1$
-44079432	$9-(8^7-6+5^4*3)*21$	-46006281	$-9*((87/6+5)*4^3)^2+1$
-44079450	$-9-(8^7-6+5^4*3)*21$	-46057554	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1))$
-44079684	$9-(8^7+6+5^4*3)*21$	-46057698	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1))$
-44079702	$-9-(8^7+6+5^4*3)*21$	-46061469	$9*(8-(7^6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1))$
-44229809	$(9*8+7)*(-6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^2+1$	-46061613	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1))$
-44229967	$(-9*8-7)*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3))^2+1$	-46110274	$-98*((7^6-5)*4-3*21)$
-44276433	$9-(8^7+6*5^4*3)*21$	-46113214	$-98*((7^6-5)*4-32-1)$
-44469360	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*(43-2+1))$	-46113410	$-98*((7^6-5)*4-32+1)$
-44469504	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*(43-2+1))$	-46114194	$-98*((7^6+5)*4-3*21)$
-44470965	$(9+8-7^6*54/3)*21$	-46115468	$98*((7^6-5)*-4+3^2+1)$
-44471077	$(9+(8-7^6*54)/3)*21$	-46115664	$98*((7^6-5)*-4+3^2-1)$
-44471145	$9+(8-7^6*54/3)*21$	-46115762	$-98*((7^6-5)*4-3*2-1)$
-44471163	$-9+(8-7^6*54/3)*21$	-46116105	$-98*((7^6-5)*4-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-44471189	$(9-(8+7^6*54)/3)*21$	-46116133	$-98*((7^6-5)*4-3)+21$
-44471257	$9+(8-7^6*54)/3*21$	-46116175	$-98*((7^6-5)*4-3)-21$
-44471301	$(9-8-7^6*54/3)*21$	-46116203	$-98*((7^6-5)*4-3/2-1)$
-44471343	$(9-8+7^6*54/3)*-21$	-46116399	$-98*((7^6-5)*4-3/2+1)$
-44471369	$9-(8+7^6*54)/3*21$	-46116434	$-98*((7^6-5)*4-3/21)$
-44471455	$(-9+(8-7^6*54)/3)*21$	-46116462	$-98*((7^6-5)*4+3/21)$
-44471481	$9-(8+7^6*54/3)*21$	-46116497	$-98*((7^6-5)*4+3/2-1)$
-44471499	$-9-(8+7^6*54/3)*21$	-46116693	$-98*((7^6-5)*4+3/2+1)$
-44471567	$(9+(8+7^6*54)/3)*-21$	-46116721	$-98*((7^6-5)*4+3)+21$
-44471679	$(9+8+7^6*54/3)*-21$	-46116763	$-98*((7^6-5)*4+3)-21$
-44473140	$9*(8-(7^6+5)*(43-2+1))$	-46116791	$-98*((7^6-5)*4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-44473284	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*(43-2+1))$	-46117134	$-98*((7^6+5)*4-32-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-46117428	$-98 * ((7^6 - 5) * 4 + 3^2 + 1)$	-48708684	$9 * (8 - (7^6 + 5) * (43 + 2 + 1))$
-46118114	$-98 * (7^6 * (5 - 4 + 3) - 2 - 1)$	-48708828	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 5) * (43 + 2 + 1))$
-46118192	$(-98 * 7^6 + 54) * (3 + 2 - 1)$	-48904240	$-98 / (7 / ((6 - 5^4 * 3)^2 - 1))$
-46118359	$98 * (7^6 * (-5 + 4 - 3) + 2^2 - 1)$	-48904268	$-98 / (7 / ((6 - 5^4 * 3)^2 + 1))$
-46118457	$98 * (7^6 * (-5 + 4 - 3) - 2^2 - 1)$	-48941967	$9 - 8 * (7^6 * (5^4 + 32) - 1)$
-46118624	$(-98 * 7^6 - 54) * (3 + 2 - 1)$	-49020792	$(9 + 8) * (7 - (6 + 5) * 4^3 + 2 + 1)$
-46118702	$-98 * (7^6 * (5 - 4 + 3) + 2 + 1)$	-49020826	$(9 + 8) * (7 - (6 + 5) * 4^3 + 2 - 1)$
-46119388	$98 * ((7^6 + 5) * -4 + 3^2 + 1)$	-49021030	$(-9 - 8) * (7 + (6 + 5) * 4^3 + 2 - 1)$
-46119682	$-98 * ((7^6 - 5) * 4 + 32 + 1)$	-49021064	$(-9 - 8) * (7 + (6 + 5) * 4^3 + 2 + 1)$
-46120025	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 - 3 - 2^2 - 1)$	-49190095	$9^8 - (7 * (6 - 5^4))^2 + (3 + 2 - 1)$
-46120053	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 - 3) + 21$	-49411836	$9 + ((8 - 7^6 * 5)^4 + 3) * 21$
-46120095	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 - 3) - 21$	-49411962	$9 + ((8 - 7^6 * 5)^4 - 3) * 21$
-46120123	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 - 3 / 2 - 1)$	-49412340	$9 + (8 - 7^6 * 5^4 + 3) * 21$
-46120319	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 - 3 / 2 + 1)$	-49412358	$-9 + (8 - 7^6 * 5^4 + 3) * 21$
-46120354	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 - 3 / 21)$	-49412419	$98 - (7^6 * 5^4 - 3) * 21$
-46120382	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 + 3 / 21)$	-49412466	$9 + (8 - 7^6 * 5^4 - 3) * 21$
-46120417	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 + 3 / 2 - 1)$	-49412545	$98 - (7^6 * 5^4 + 3) * 21$
-46120613	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 + 3 / 2 + 1)$	-49412563	$9 - 8 * (7^6 * (54 - 3 / 2) - 1)$
-46120641	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 + 3) + 21$	-49412579	$9 - 8 * (7^6 * (54 - 3 / 2) + 1)$
-46120683	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 + 3) - 21$	-49412581	$-9 - 8 * (7^6 * (54 - 3 / 2) - 1)$
-46120711	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 + 3 + 2^2 - 1)$	-49412597	$-9 - 8 * (7^6 * (54 - 3 / 2) + 1)$
-46121054	$-98 * (7^6 * 5^4 + 3^2 + 1)$	-49412615	$-98 - (7^6 * 5^4 - 3) * 21$
-46121152	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 + 3^2 - 1)$	-49412676	$9 - (8 + 7^6 * 5^4 - 3) * 21$
-46121348	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 + 3^2 + 1)$	-49412741	$-98 - (7^6 * 5^4 + 3) * 21$
-46122622	$-98 * ((7^6 - 5) * 4 + 3^2 + 1)$	-49412802	$9 - (8 + 7^6 * 5^4 + 3) * 21$
-46123406	$-98 * (7^6 * 5^4 + 3^2 - 1)$	-49413180	$9 - ((8 + 7^6 * 5) * 4 - 3) * 21$
-46123602	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 + 32 + 1)$	-49413198	$-9 - ((8 + 7^6 * 5) * 4 - 3) * 21$
-46126542	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4 + 3^2 * 21)$	-49413306	$9 - ((8 + 7^6 * 5) * 4 + 3) * 21$
-46399311	$(-9 - 876) / 5 * (4^3 + 2 - 1)$	-49534268	$98 / (7 / ((6 + 5^4 * 3)^2 + 2 + 1))$
-46399665	$(-9 - 876) / 5 * (4^3 + 2 + 1)$	-49778307	$9^8 * (-76 / 54 / 3^2 - 1)$
-46483644	$(9 + 8) * (7 * (6 - 5^4 + (3/2))) + 1$	-49810754	$-98 * (7^6 + 5^4 + (3/2) - 1)$
-46483678	$(9 + 8) * (7 * (6 - 5^4 + (3/2))) - 1$	-49810950	$-98 * (7^6 + 5^4 + (3/2) + 1)$
-46485072	$(-9 - 8) * (7 * (6 + 5^4 + (3/2))) - 1$	-49968559	$(-9 - 8) * (7 / (6^5 / 4 / 3)^2 - 2 - 1)$
-46485106	$(-9 - 8) * (7 * (6 + 5^4 + (3/2))) + 1$	-49968593	$(-9 - 8) * (7 / (6^5 / 4 / 3)^2 - 2 + 1)$
-46858056	$-9 / 8 * 7 * (65^4 / 3 + 21)$	-49992495	$(98 - 7^6 * 5) * (4^3 + 21)$
-47059370	$(-9 - 8 * (7^6 * 5 - 4)) * (3^2 + 1)$	-49998700	$(-9 - 8) * (7^6 - 5) * (4^3 * 2 + 1)$
-47059527	$9 * (8 - 7^6 / (5^4 / 3)^2 - 1) + 1$	-50000136	$9 + (8 - 7^6 * 5) * (4^3 + 21)$
-47059529	$9 * (8 - 7^6 / (5^4 / 3)^2 - 1) - 1$	-50000468	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^6 * 5 - 4) * (3 + 2) - 1)$
-47059671	$-9 * (8 + 7^6 / (5^4 / 3)^2 - 1) + 1$	-50000502	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^6 * 5 - 4) * (3 + 2) + 1)$
-47059673	$-9 * (8 + 7^6 / (5^4 / 3)^2 - 1) - 1$	-50000727	$98 - 7^6 * 5 * (4^3 + 21)$
-47059830	$(9 - 8 * (7^6 * 5 + 4)) * (3^2 + 1)$	-50000923	$-98 - 7^6 * 5 * (4^3 + 21)$
-47257371	$9 * (8 - (7 / (6 / 54))^3) * 21$	-50001148	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^6 * 5 + 4) * (3 + 2) - 1)$
-47258811	$9 * (8 - (7 / (6 / 54))^3) * 21$	-50001182	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^6 * 5 + 4) * (3 + 2) + 1)$
-47258955	$-9 * (8 + (7 / (6 / 54))^3) * 21$	-50001496	$9 - (8 + 7^6 * 5) * (4^3 + 21)$
-47645883	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 - 5) * (43 + 2) - 1)$	-50001514	$-9 - (8 + 7^6 * 5) * (4^3 + 21)$
-47645901	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 - 5) * (43 + 2) + 1)$	-50002950	$(-9 - 8) * (7^6 + 5) * (4^3 * 2 + 1)$
-47647448	$9 * (8 - (7^6 * 5 - 4) * 3^2) + 1$	-50009155	$(98 + 7^6 * 5) * (-4^3 - 21)$
-47647450	$9 * (8 - (7^6 * 5 - 4) * 3^2) - 1$	-50312816	$-9 * (8^7 + (6 - 5^4 * 3)^2) + 1$
-47647592	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 * 5 - 4) * 3^2) + 1$	-50312818	$-9 * (8^7 + (6 - 5^4 * 3)^2) - 1$
-47647594	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 * 5 - 4) * 3^2) - 1$	-50353763	$9 - 8 * 7^6 * (54 - 3 / 2 + 1)$
-47648096	$9 * (8 - (7^6 * 5 + 4) * 3^2) + 1$	-50689903	$9 - 8 * 7^6 * (54 - 3 / 21)$
-47648098	$9 * (8 - (7^6 * 5 + 4) * 3^2) - 1$	-50689921	$-9 - 8 * 7^6 * (54 - 3 / 21)$
-47648240	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4) * 3^2) + 1$	-50704547	$9 + 8 - (7^6 - 5) * (432 - 1)$
-47648242	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 * 5 + 4) * 3^2) - 1$	-50704563	$9 - 8 - (7^6 - 5) * (432 - 1)$
-47649933	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 5) * (43 + 2) - 1)$	-50704565	$-9 + 8 - (7^6 - 5) * (432 - 1)$
-47649951	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 + 5) * (43 + 2) + 1)$	-50704581	$-9 - 8 - (7^6 - 5) * (432 - 1)$
-47978760	$(-9 - 8) * (7^6 - 54) * (3 + 21)$	-50708857	$9 + 8 - (7^6 + 5) * (432 - 1)$
-47998735	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^6 - 5) * 4^3 * 2 - 1)$	-50708873	$9 - 8 - (7^6 + 5) * (432 - 1)$
-47998769	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^6 - 5) * 4^3 * 2 + 1)$	-50708875	$-9 + 8 - (7^6 + 5) * (432 - 1)$
-48000765	$(9 - 8 / 7^6 - 6 * (5^4 - 3)) * (2 + 1)$	-50708891	$-9 - 8 - (7^6 + 5) * (432 - 1)$
-48000779	$9 - 8 * (7^6 * (54 - 3) - 2^2 - 1)$	-50717816	$-9 * (8^7 + (6 + 5^4 * 3)^2) + 1$
-48000787	$9 - 8 * (7^6 * (54 - 3) + 2^2 - 1)$	-50717818	$-9 * (8^7 + (6 + 5^4 * 3)^2) - 1$
-48000797	$-9 - 8 * (7^6 * (54 - 3) - 2^2 - 1)$	-50823584	$(98 - 7^6 * 54) * (3^2 - 1)$
-48000805	$-9 - 8 * (7^6 * (54 - 3) + 2^2 - 1)$	-50824251	$-9 * (8 + 7^6 * (5 + 43) - 21)$
-48000819	$(-9 - 8 / 7^6 - 6 * (5^4 - 3)) * (2 + 1)$	-50824270	$98 - 7^6 * 54 * (3^2 - 1)$
-48002815	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^6 + 5) * 4^3 * 2 - 1)$	-50824275	$9 * (8 - 7^6 * (5 + 43)) + 21$
-48002849	$(-9 - 8) * ((7^6 + 5) * 4^3 * 2 + 1)$	-50824317	$9 * (8 - 7^6 * (5 + 43)) - 21$
-48022824	$(-9 - 8) * (7^6 + 54) * (3 + 21)$	-50824331	$9 - 8 * (7^6 * 54 - 3 - 2^2 - 1)$
-48287109	$(-9 - 876 / 5) * (4^3 + 2 + 1)$	-50824405	$-9 - 8 * (7^6 * 54 + 3 + 2^2 - 1)$
-48428073	$(9^8 + 7^6 * 5) * (-4 / 32 - 1)$	-50824419	$-9 * (8 + 7^6 * (5 + 43)) + 21$
-48704544	$9 * (8 - (7^6 - 5) * (43 + 2 + 1))$	-50824461	$-9 * (8 + 7^6 * (5 + 43)) - 21$
-48704688	$-9 * (8 + (7^6 - 5) * (43 + 2 + 1))$	-50824466	$-98 - 7^6 * 54 * (3^2 - 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-50824467	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)+2+1)$	-55059795	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+32)-1)$
-50824485	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)-21)$	-55059813	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+32)+1)$
-50825152	$(-98-7^{\wedge}6*54)*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-55487592	$-9*((8^*76+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-50837181	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)*21$	-55487610	$-9*((8^*76+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-50939835	$9+8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432+1)$	-55527959	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-3*21)$
-50939851	$9-8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432+1)$	-55527977	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-3*21)$
-50939853	$-9+8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432+1)$	-55530024	$9+(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-3*21)$
-50939869	$-9-8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(432+1)$	-55530151	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+21)$
-50944165	$9+8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432+1)$	-55530169	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+21)$
-50944181	$9-8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432+1)$	-55530487	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-21)$
-50944183	$-9+8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432+1)$	-55530505	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-21)$
-50944199	$-9-8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(432+1)$	-55530614	$9+(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-3*21)$
-50958815	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/21)$	-55532679	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-3*21)$
-50958833	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/21)$	-56010455	$9*(8-(7^*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)^*2)+1$
-51168789	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43^*2+1)$	-56010457	$9*(8-(7^*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)^*2)-1$
-51176610	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43^*2+1)$	-56010599	$-9*(8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)^*2)+1$
-51177217	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(43^*2+1)$	-56010601	$-9*(8+(7^*6)^{\wedge}(5-4+3)^*2)-1$
-51177413	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5*(43^*2+1)$	-56042378	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
-51178002	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(43^*2+1)$	-56118636	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3+2)-1)$
-51185841	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(-43^*2-1)$	-56118654	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3+2)+1)$
-51225482	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	-56469168	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*5*4)*(3+21)$
-51710472	$-9*((87*6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-56470743	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*4*(3+21)$
-51710490	$-9*((87*6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-56471319	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*4)*(3+21)$
-51765461	$(9-8/7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^*3-2+1)$	-56471337	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*4)*(3+21)$
-51765659	$(-9-8/7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^*3-2+1)$	-56471375	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4/-3+2)+1$
-51882964	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)/2-1)$	-56471377	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4/-3+2)-1$
-51883258	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)/2-1)$	-56471422	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*4*(3+21)$
-51883454	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)/2+1)$	-56471475	$(-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4-3))*(2+1)$
-51904314	$-9*(87-65)*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	-56471565	$(9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4+3))*(2+1)$
-51904710	$-9*(87-65)*(4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	-56471618	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*5*4*(3+21)$
-52000841	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3*2)-1)$	-56471663	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4/-3-2)+1$
-52000875	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3*2)+1)$	-56471665	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4/-3-2)-1$
-52236139	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2)-1)$	-56471703	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*4)*(3+21)$
-52236155	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2)+1)$	-56472279	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*4*(3+21)$
-52236157	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2)-1)$	-56472297	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*4*(3+21)$
-52236173	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2)+1)$	-56473872	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*5*4)*(-3-21)$
-53307810	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6/5*(4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	-56822409	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3))^*21$
-53647931	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-56824290	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3))^*21$
-53647939	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-56824369	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3)*21$
-53647949	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-56824565	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3)*21$
-53647957	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-56824626	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3))^*21$
-54000630	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+21)$	-56826525	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3))^*21$
-54000774	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)-21)$	-57026079	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/21))$
-54000798	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))+21$	-57026223	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/21))$
-54000840	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))-21$	-57059667	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(54^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-54000936	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)-2-1)$	-57059863	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(54^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-54000942	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))+21$	-57118096	$(-9-8)*((7^*6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-54000954	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)-2+1)$	-57118130	$(-9-8)*((7^*6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-54000972	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+2-1)$	-57176775	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54+3*21)$
-54000984	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))-21$	-57176919	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54-3*21)$
-54000990	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+2+1)$	-57177045	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54+32+1)$
-54001008	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)-21)$	-57177063	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54+32-1)$
-54001152	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+21)$	-57177126	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54+3+21)$
-54253473	$-9^{\wedge}8(-8+7)*(6+5^{\wedge}4(4^*3)^*2+1)$	-57177180	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54-3+21)$
-54263737	$9*(8+(7-6*5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-57177189	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54-32-1)$
-54263879	$9*(-8+(7-6*5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-57177207	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54-32+1)$
-54263881	$9*(-8+(7-6*5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-57177252	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54+3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-54735876	$-9*(8+76/5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-57177294	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54+3)+21$
-55049932	$98-7^*6*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-57177450	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54-3-2+1)$
-55050100	$98-7^*6*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-57177522	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54+3+2-1)$
-55050135	$98-7*(6^*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-57177534	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54+3)-21$
-55050149	$98-7*(6^*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-57177549	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)-3*21$
-55050161	$9*8-7*(6^*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-57177576	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54+3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-55050175	$9*8-7*(6^*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-57177621	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54-32+1)$
-55050184	$98-7^*6*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-57177639	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54-32-1)$
-55050233	$(-9+8)*7*(6^*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-57177648	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54-3+21)$
-55050247	$(-9+8)*7*(6^*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-57177702	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54+3+21)$
-55050305	$9*-8-7*(6^*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-57177765	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54+32-1)$
-55050319	$9*-8-7*(6^*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-57177783	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54+32+1)$
-55050331	$-98-7*(6^*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-57177909	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54-3*21)$
-55050345	$-98-7*(6^*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-57178053	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54+3*21)$
-55050352	$98-7^*6*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-57246504	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-57246700	$98*(7^6*5+(4^3)^2-1)$	-57648388	$-98*(7^6*5+4-3/21)$
-57294965	$98-7^6*(54*3^2+1)$	-57648416	$-98*(7^6*5+4+3/21)$
-57295161	$-98-7^6*(54*3^2+1)$	-57648451	$-98*(7^6*5+4+3/2-1)$
-57328605	$9*(8-7^6*(54+3/21))$	-57648465	$-98*(7^6*5+4)-3*21$
-57328749	$-9*(8+7^6*(54+3/21))$	-57648647	$-98*(7^6*5+4+3/2+1)$
-57341662	$-98*((7^6-5^4)*(3+2)-1)$	-57648675	$-98*(7^6*5+4+3)+21$
-57341858	$-98*((7^6-5^4)*(3+2)+1)$	-57648717	$-98*(7^6*5+4+3)-21$
-57394147	$((9^8*-7-6^5)^4-3)/21$	-57648745	$-98*(7^6*5+4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-57397109	$((9^8*-7-6^5)^4+3)/21$	-57649137	$-98*(7^6*5+4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-57466710	$-98*(7^6*5-43^2-1)$	-57649165	$-98*(7^6*5+4*3)+21$
-57466906	$-98*(7^6*5-43^2+1)$	-57649207	$-98*(7^6*5+4*3)-21$
-57478666	$98*(7^6*5+(4^3)^{(2+1)})$	-57649235	$-98*(7^6*5+4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-57513726	$9^8*((7/6+(5+4)^{-3})^{-2+1})$	-57649872	$-98*(7^6*5+4*(3+2)-1)$
-57516298	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3*21)$	-57650019	$-98*(7^6*5+4*3-2-1)$
-57621452	$-98*((7^6-54)*(3+2)-1)$	-57650215	$-98*(7^6*5+4+3/2+1)$
-57621648	$-98*((7^6-54)*(3+2)+1)$	-57650558	$98*((7^6+5)*(4-3^2)-1)$
-57629194	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3*(2+1))$	-57650656	$-98*(7^6*5-4+3-2-1)$
-57633800	$98*(7^6*5+(4^3)^2+1)$	-57650852	$-98*(7^6*5-4+3+2+1)$
-57633996	$98*(7^6*5+(4^3)^2-1)$	-57651244	$-98*(7^6*5+4*3+2+1)$
-57635074	$-98*(7^6*5-4*(3+2+1))$	-57651440	$-98*(7^6*5+4+3-2-1)$
-57635858	$-98*(7^6*5-4*(3+2-1))$	-57651636	$-98*(7^6*5+4+3+2+1)$
-57637426	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3*(2+1))$	-57652175	$-98*(7^6*5+4+3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-57638112	$-98*((7^6-5^4)*(3+2)-1)$	-57652273	$-98*(7^6*5+4+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-57638308	$-98*((7^6-5^4)*(3+2)+1)$	-57652714	$-98*(7^6*5+(4+3)^2-1)$
-57638602	$-98*(7^6*5-4*(3+2+1))$	-57652910	$-98*(7^6*5+(4+3)^2+1)$
-57640954	$-98*(7^6*5+4*(3-2+1))$	-57653792	$-98*(7^6*5-4+3*2+1)$
-57641444	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3-2-1)$	-57653988	$-98*(7^6*5+4^3-2-1)$
-57641640	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3-2+1)$	-57654184	$-98*(7^6*5+4^3-2+1)$
-57641689	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-57654233	$-98*(7^6*5+4^3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-57641717	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3)+21$	-57654261	$-98*(7^6*5+4^3)+21$
-57641759	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3)-21$	-57654303	$-98*(7^6*5+4^3)-21$
-57641787	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-57654331	$-98*(7^6*5+4^3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-57641836	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3+2-1)$	-57654380	$-98*(7^6*5+4^3+2-1)$
-57642032	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3+2+1)$	-57654576	$-98*(7^6*5+4^3+2+1)$
-57642228	$-98*(7^6*5+4-3*2+1)$	-57655066	$-98*(7^6*5-4*(3-2+1))$
-57643110	$98*(7^6*5+(4+3)^2+1)$	-57657418	$-98*(7^6*5+4*(3+2+1))$
-57643306	$98*(7^6*5+(4+3)^2-1)$	-57657712	$-98*((7^6+5^4)*(3+2)-1)$
-57643747	$-98*(7^6*5-43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-57657908	$-98*((7^6+5^4)*(3+2)+1)$
-57643845	$-98*(7^6*5-43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-57658594	$-98*(7^6*5+4^3*(2+1))$
-57644384	$-98*(7^6*5-4-3-2-1)$	-57660162	$-98*(7^6*5+4*(3-2+1))$
-57644580	$-98*(7^6*5-4-3+2+1)$	-57660946	$-98*(7^6*5+4*(3+2+1))$
-57644776	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3-2+1)$	-57662024	$-98*(7^6*5+(4^3)^2-1)$
-57645168	$-98*(7^6*5+4-3-2-1)$	-57662220	$-98*(7^6*5+(4^3)^2+1)$
-57645364	$-98*(7^6*5+4-3+2+1)$	-57666826	$-98*(7^6*5+4^3*(2+1))$
-57645462	$98*((7^6-5)*(4-3^2)+1)$	-57671539	$9-(8^7/(6/5)-4)*(3+2+1)$
-57645805	$-98*(7^6*5-43/2-1)$	-57671803	$9-(8^7/(6/5)+4)*(3+2+1)$
-57646001	$-98*(7^6*5-43/2+1)$	-57671821	$-9-(8^7/(6/5)+4)*(3+2+1)$
-57646148	$-98*(7^6*5-4*(3+2)+1)$	-57674372	$-98*((7^6+54)*(3+2)-1)$
-57646785	$-98*(7^6*5-4*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-57674568	$-98*((7^6+54)*(3+2)+1)$
-57646813	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3)+21$	-57779722	$-98*(7^6*5+4^3*2+1)$
-57646855	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3)-21$	-57808971	$9^8*((-7+6/5+4)^{-3*2}-1)$
-57646883	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-57817354	$-98*(7^6*5+(4^3)^2+1)$
-57647275	$-98*(7^6*5-4-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-57829114	$98*(7^6*5-43^2+1)$
-57647303	$-98*(7^6*5-4-3)+21$	-57829310	$98*(7^6*5-43^2-1)$
-57647345	$-98*(7^6*5-4-3)-21$	-57932702	$(9+8)*((7+6)*(5-4^3^2)+1)$
-57647373	$-98*(7^6*5-4-3/2-1)$	-57932736	$(9+8)*((7+6)*(5-4^3^2)-1)$
-57647555	$-98*(7^6*5-4)+3*21$	-57934912	$(-9-8)*((7+6)*(5+4^3^2)-1)$
-57647569	$-98*(7^6*5-4-3/2+1)$	-57954162	$-98*((7^6+5^4)*(3+2)-1)$
-57647604	$-98*(7^6*5-4-3/2+1)$	-57954358	$-98*((7^6+5^4)*(3+2)+1)$
-57647632	$-98*(7^6*5-4+3/2+1)$	-58000940	$(9+8)*(-7^6*(5+4^3*2)+1)$
-57647681	$-98*(7^6*5-4)-3*21$	-58000974	$(9+8)*(-7^6*(5+4^3*2)-1)$
-57647863	$-98*7^6*5+(4+3)*21$	-58049320	$-98*(7^6*5+(4^3)^2-1)$
-57647891	$-98*(7^6*5-4+3)+21$	-58049516	$-98*(7^6*5+(4^3)^2+1)$
-57647898	$-98*(7^6*5-4/(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	-58236318	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+3-2)-1)$
-57647933	$-98*(7^6*5-4+3)-21$	-58236336	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+3-2)+1)$
-57647938	$-98*7^6*5-4*(3-2+1)$	-58939731	$(-9-8)*((7+6-5^4*3)^2-1)$
-57648082	$-98*7^6*5+4*(3-2+1)$	-58939765	$(-9-8)*((7+6-5^4*3)^2+1)$
-57648087	$-98*(7^6*5+4-3)+21$	-59253642	$-98*(7^6*5+4^{\wedge}(3*2+1))$
-57648122	$-98*(7^6*5+4/(3+2^{\wedge}-1))$	-59255712	$9-(8*7^6-5^4)*3*21$
-57648129	$-98*(7^6*5+4-3)-21$	-59255730	$-9-(8*7^6-5^4)*3*21$
-57648157	$-98*(7^6*5+4-3/2-1)$	-59267871	$9-8*(7^6-54)*3*21$
-57648339	$-98*(7^6*5+4)+3*21$	-59267889	$-9-8*(7^6-54)*3*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-59290551	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5 \cdot 4)^*3^*21$	-61603511	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6 \cdot 5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-59290569	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5 \cdot 4)^*3^*21$	-61603605	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6 \cdot 5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-59291505	$(9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6 - 54)^*3)^*21$	-61603793	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6 \cdot 5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-59291883	$(9+(8^*7^{\wedge}6 - 54)^*3)^*-21$	-61603887	$(9 \cdot 8^*7)^*(6+5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-59292315	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5) \cdot 4)^*3^*21$	-61604169	$(9 \cdot 8^*7)^*(6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-59292387	$-9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5)^*(4+3) \cdot 21)$	-61725960	$-9^*(8+7^*6^{\wedge}(5+4 \cdot 3)^*21)$
-59292819	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5)+4)^*3^*21$	-61972565	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 54)^*(32-1)$
-59292837	$-9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5)+4)^*3^*21$	-62029481	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*(32-1)$
-59293827	$9 \cdot (8/7^{\wedge}6 - 5 \cdot 4)^*3^*21$	-62076728	$-98^*((7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-59294088	$-9^*8^*((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)^*(4+3)+21)$	-62076924	$-98^*((7+6)^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-59294583	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5+4)^*3^*21$	-62177492	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 765)^*(-4/3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-59295591	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5 \cdot 4)^*3^*21$	-62179702	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)^*(-4/3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-59295717	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)^*3^*21$	-62468892	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-3^*21))$
-59297355	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5) \cdot 4)^*3^*21$	-62469036	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-3^*21))$
-59297859	$9 \cdot (8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)+4)^*3^*21$	-62471358	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+21)$
-59298309	$(9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3)^*21$	-62471502	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+21)$
-59298687	$(9+(8^*7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3)^*-21$	-62471528	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2)^+1$
-59299623	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*3^*21$	-62471530	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2) \cdot -1$
-59322303	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3^*21$	-62471564	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3) \cdot 2)+1$
-59322321	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3^*21$	-62471566	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3) \cdot 2) \cdot -1$
-59334462	$9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3^*21$	-62471672	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2)+1$
-59334480	$-9 \cdot (8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3^*21$	-62471674	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2) \cdot -1$
-59383601	$(9+8)^*(7 \cdot (6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-62471708	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3) \cdot 2)+1$
-59383635	$(9+8)^*(7 \cdot (6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-62471710	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3) \cdot 2) \cdot -1$
-59383839	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7+(6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-62471736	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3) \cdot 21)$
-59383873	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7+(6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-62471880	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}3) \cdot 21)$
-59610087	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3^*21$	-62473096	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^*6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-59610105	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*3^*21$	-62473130	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^*6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-59698464	$-9^*8^*7^{\wedge}6^*(5+43/21)$	-62474202	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-3^*21))$
-59701875	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7 \cdot 6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-62474346	$9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-3^*21))$
-59701909	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7 \cdot 6-5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-62510058	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^{\wedge}6^*543)^*(2+1)$
-59829375	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7 \cdot 6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-62602081	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-43^*21)$
-59829409	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7 \cdot 6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-62911671	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)^*4-321)$
-60000565	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5 \cdot 4)^*3^*2-1)$	-62917449	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)^*4+321)$
-60000599	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5 \cdot 4)^*3^*2+1)$	-63410018	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3/2) \cdot -1)$
-60000973	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4^*3/2-1)$	-63410214	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3/2)+1)$
-60001007	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4^*3/2+1)$	-63412713	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+(4-3)/2) \cdot -1)$
-60001381	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4)^*3^*2-1)$	-63412909	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+(4-3)/2)+1)$
-60001415	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4)^*3^*2+1)$	-63415408	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3/2) \cdot -1)$
-60148601	$(9+8)^*(7 \cdot (6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-63415604	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3/2)+1)$
-60148635	$(9+8)^*(7 \cdot (6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-63468889	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7)^*(65^{\wedge}4^*32+1)$
-60148839	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7+(6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-63529353	$(9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-60148873	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*(7+(6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-63529480	$(98-7^{\wedge}6^*54)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-60233551	$9 \cdot 8^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-63529577	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4^*3+2)+1$
-60233569	$-9 \cdot 8^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-63529579	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4^*3+2) \cdot -1$
-60233887	$9 \cdot 8^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-63529613	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4^*3-2)+1$
-60233905	$-9 \cdot 8^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-63529615	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4^*3-2) \cdot -1$
-60238671	$9 \cdot 8^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-63529839	$(-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-60239007	$9 \cdot 8^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-63530225	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4)^*3+2)+1$
-60239025	$-9 \cdot 8^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-63530227	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4)^*3+2) \cdot -1$
-60353676	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(54+3)+21)$	-63530261	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4)^*3-2)+1$
-60353820	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(54+3) \cdot 21)$	-63530263	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4)^*3-2) \cdot -1$
-60353844	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(54+3))^+21$	-63530369	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4^*3+2)+1$
-60353886	$-9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(54+3)) \cdot -21$	-63530371	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*54)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-60353982	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(54+3) \cdot 2-1)$	-63530549	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4^*3+2)+1$
-60353988	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(54+3))^+21$	-63530551	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4^*3+2) \cdot -1$
-60354030	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(54+3)) \cdot -21$	-63530657	$9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4)^*3-2)+1$
-60354036	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(54+3)+2+1)$	-63530659	$9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4)^*3-2) \cdot -1$
-60354054	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(54+3) \cdot 21)$	-63530693	$-9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4)^*3+2)+1$
-60354198	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(54+3)+21)$	-63530695	$-9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4)^*3+2) \cdot -1$
-60471577	$9 \cdot 8^*7^{\wedge}6^*(5/4+3^*21)$	-63531081	$(9 \cdot (8+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-60521664	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4 \cdot 3)^*21$	-63531305	$9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4^*3+2)+1$
-60526809	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4 \cdot 3)^*21$	-63531307	$9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4^*3+2) \cdot -1$
-60534012	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/4+3)^*21$	-63531341	$-9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4^*3+2)+1$
-60539157	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)/4+3)^*21$	-63531343	$-9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4^*3+2) \cdot -1$
-60597231	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7+6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-63531440	$(-98-7^{\wedge}6^*54)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-60597265	$(-9 \cdot 8)^*((7+6+5^{\wedge}4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-63531567	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*4)^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-60702372	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2) \cdot -1)$	-63699534	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-60820470	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-63702450	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-61174555	$(9 \cdot 8^*7^{\wedge}6/5)^*(4+321)$	-63765686	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6^*(543-2+1)$
-61180405	$(9+8^*7^{\wedge}6/5)^*(-4-321)$	-63765830	$-9^*8-7^{\wedge}6^*(543-2+1)$
-61603323	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6-5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-63778571	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5+43^*21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-63971663	$(-9-8)*((7^6-54)*32-1)$	-69145762	$-98*((7^6-54)*3*2-1)$
-63971697	$(-9-8)*((7^6-54)*32+1)$	-69145958	$-98*((7^6-54)*3*2+1)$
-63998319	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)*4^3/2-1)$	-69175304	$9*8/-7*((6^5+4)/3)^2-1)$
-63998353	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)*4^3/2+1)$	-69175554	$-98*(7^6*(5+4-3)-21)$
-64000984	$9*8-7^6*(543+2-1)$	-69177318	$-98*(7^6*(5+4-3)-2-1)$
-64001128	$-9*8-7^6*(543+2-1)$	-69177563	$98*(7^6*(-5-4+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-64003759	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5)*4^3/2-1)$	-69177661	$98*(7^6*(-5-4+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-64003793	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5)*4^3/2+1)$	-69177906	$-98*(7^6*(5+4-3)+2+1)$
-64030415	$(-9-8)*((7^6+54)*32-1)$	-69178249	$-98*((7^6+5/4)*3*2-1)$
-64030449	$(-9-8)*((7^6+54)*32+1)$	-69179670	$-98*(7^6*(5+4-3)+21)$
-64070538	$-98*(7^6*5+4^{\wedge}(3^2-1))$	-69209266	$-98*((7^6+54)*3*2-1)$
-64236282	$9*8-7^6*(543+2+1)$	-69209462	$-98*((7^6+54)*3*2+1)$
-64236426	$-9*8-7^6*(543+2+1)$	-69545014	$-98*((7^6+5^{\wedge}4)*3*2-1)$
-64540557	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)/2-1)$	-69545210	$-98*((7^6+5^{\wedge}4)*3*2+1)$
-64599606	$9^{\wedge}8*((7-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)/-2-1)$	-69648110	$98-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4-32-1)$
-64942071	$9-8*(7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-21)$	-69648306	$-98-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4-32-1)$
-64942089	$-9-8*(7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-21)$	-69883408	$98-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4-32+1)$
-64942221	$(-9-8)*((7^6+54)*32+1)$	-69883604	$-98-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4-32+1)$
-64942275	$(-9-8/7^{\wedge}-6*(5*4+3))*^2+1)$	-69896319	$9^{\wedge}8-7^6*5*4^{\wedge}3*(2+1)$
-64942407	$9-8*(7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+21)$	-70001104	$(9+8)*7^6*5*(4+3)+2+1)$
-64942425	$-9-8*(7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+21)$	-70001206	$(-9-8)*(7^6*5*(4+3)+2+1)$
-65674288	$(-9/(8*(7^6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2)))^{\wedge}-1$	-70286823	$-9/(8/(7*(65^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1))$
-65970795	$(-9-8)*(7^6-54)*(32+1)$	-70589265	$(9-8/7^{\wedge}-6*5)*^2*(4*3+2+1)$
-66001072	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5*(4+3)-2)-1)$	-70589535	$(-9-8/7^{\wedge}-6*5)*^2*(4*3+2+1)$
-66001106	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5*(4+3)-2)+1)$	-70778375	$9*(8*7-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-66031383	$(-9-8)*(7^6+54)*(32+1)$	-70778377	$9*(8*7-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-66118640	$98-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4-3*21)$	-70778746	$9*(8+7-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-66118836	$-98-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4-3*21)$	-70778870	$9*(8-7-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-66624649	$(-9-8)*7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)*2-1)$	-70778872	$9*(8-7-6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-66624887	$(-9-8)*7*(6^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)*2+1)$	-70778888	$-9*(8-7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-66674853	$9*(8-(7^6-54)*3)*21$	-70778890	$-9*(8-7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-66676293	$9*(8-(7^6-54)*3*21)$	-70779014	$-9*(8+7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-66676437	$-9*(8+(7^6-54)*3*21)$	-70779016	$-9*(8+7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-66677877	$-9*(8+(7^6-54)*3)*21$	-70779383	$-9*(8*7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-66701808	$9*(8-(7^6-5-4)*3*21)$	-70779385	$-9*(8*7+6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-66701952	$-9*(8+(7^6-5-4)*3*21)$	-70779609	$-9*(87+6*(5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-66704925	$(98-7^6*(5+4)*3)*21$	-70779672	$-9*(87+6*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-66706470	$9+(8-7^6*(5+4)*3)*21$	-70779717	$-9*(87+6*(5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-66706806	$9+(8-7^6*(5+4)*3)*21$	-70779933	$-9*(87+6*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-66706824	$-9+(8-7^6*(5+4)*3)*21$	-71249745	$-9/87*((6/5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-66706885	$98-7^6*(5+4)*3*21$	-71530591	$9+8*(7^6*(5-43)*2-1)$
-66707081	$-98-7^6*(5+4)*3*21$	-71548431	$((9^{\wedge}8-7^6)*5+4)/3+21$
-66707142	$9-(8+7^6*(5+4)*3)*21$	-71548473	$((9^{\wedge}8-7^6)*5+4)/3-21$
-66707496	$-9-(8+7^6*(5+4)*3)*21$	-71679937	$(9-(8^{\wedge}(7/-6)/5)^{\wedge}-4)*(3*2+1)$
-66709041	$(98+7^6*(5+4)*3)*-21$	-71743260	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)*(4/3-2-1)$
-66712158	$-9*(8+(7^6+5+4)*3*21)$	-71744491	$((9^{\wedge}8-7-6)*5-5+4)/3+21$
-66736089	$9*(8-(7^6+54)*3)*21$	-71744517	$((9^{\wedge}8+7-6)*5-5-4)/3+21$
-66737529	$9*(8-(7^6+54)*3*21)$	-71744553	$((9^{\wedge}8-7+6)*5+5+4)/3-21$
-66737673	$-9*(8+(7^6+54)*3*21)$	-71744579	$((9^{\wedge}8+7+6)*5-5-4)/3-21$
-66739113	$-9*(8+(7^6+54)*3)*21$	-71745810	$((9^{\wedge}8+765)*(4/3-2-1)$
-66929208	$(9/(8-7^6*5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$	-71868834	$-9/8*(7^6*543+2-1)$
-67061286	$9*(8-(7^6+5^{\wedge}4)*3*21)$	-71940597	$((9^{\wedge}8+7^6)*5-5-4)/3+21$
-67061430	$-9*(8+(7^6+5^{\wedge}4)*3*21)$	-71940639	$((9^{\wedge}8+7^6)*5-5-4)/3-21$
-67762683	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-71998111	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)*4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-67762827	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-71998145	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)*4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-67763061	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-72004231	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5)*4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-67763205	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-72004265	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5)*4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-67768587	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-72011877	$(9^{\wedge}8-76^{\wedge}5/4^{\wedge}3)*-21$
-67768965	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-72133542	$-9/8*(7^6*(543+2)-1)$
-68001105	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5*4-3)*2-1)$	-72354037	$98-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-68001139	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5*4-3)*2+1)$	-72354233	$-98-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-68112000	$-9*((876+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-72589335	$98-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-68112008	$-9*(876+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1$	-72589531	$-98-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-68112009	$-9*(876+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2/1$	-72706984	$98-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4-3*2-1)$
-68112010	$-9*(876+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1$	-72707180	$-98-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4-3*2-1)$
-68112018	$-9*((876+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-72817778	$(-9/(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4*3+2))^{\wedge}-1$
-68249233	$9^{\wedge}8-7^6*(5^{\wedge}4+321)$	-72939342	$(98-7^6*5*4)*^2*(32-1)$
-68801265	$9*(8-7^6/5)*(4+321)$	-72941379	$9+(8-7^6*5)*4*(32-1)$
-68848065	$-9*(8+7^6/5)*(4+321)$	-72942123	$9+(8-7^6*5*4)*^2*(32-1)$
-68874625	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)/-5*4+3)*2+1$	-72942619	$9-(8+7^6*5*4)*^2*(32-1)$
-68874627	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)/-5*4+3)*2-1$	-72943363	$9-(8+7^6*5)*4*(32-1)$
-68874639	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)/-5*4-3)*2-1$	-72945418	$(98+7^6*5*4)*(-32+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-73059768	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+21)$	-76213440	$-9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-321)$
-73059912	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-21)$	-76232169	$-9^*((8^*7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-73059938	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+2)+1$	-76232187	$-9^*((8^*7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-73059940	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+2)-1$	-76236119	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(-5-4)+3^*2)+1$
-73059974	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-2)+1$	-76236121	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(-5-4)+3^*2)-1$
-73059976	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-2)-1$	-76236983	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(-5-4)-3^*2)+1$
-73060082	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-2)+1$	-76236985	$9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(-5-4)-3^*2)-1$
-73060084	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-2)-1$	-76238280	$-9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3+21)$
-73060118	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+2)+1$	-76238847	$-9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+32)-1)$
-73060120	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+2)-1$	-76240917	$-9^*((8^*7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-73060146	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-21)$	-76240935	$-9^*((8^*7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-73060290	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+21)$	-76259664	$-9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+321)$
-73177559	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+21$	-76271472	$-9^*8^*((7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-73177601	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-21$	-76271535	$-9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-73177755	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+21$	-76271553	$-9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-73177797	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-21$	-76271616	$-9^*8^*((7^{\wedge}6+54)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-73295255	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3+2-1)$	-77177646	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32-1)$
-73295399	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3+2-1)$	-77177842	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32-1)$
-73397907	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2-1)$	-77412944	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32+1)$
-73516005	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2+1)$	-77413140	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32+1)$
-73547334	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3/21)$	-77645106	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)^*(32+1)$
-73547530	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3/21)$	-77647275	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)^*4*(32+1)$
-73765851	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3-2+1)$	-77648067	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)^*(32+1)$
-73765995	$-9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3-2+1)$	-77648085	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)^*(32+1)$
-73883453	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+21$	-77648242	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4*(32+1)$
-73883495	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-21$	-77648438	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4*(32+1)$
-73883649	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+21$	-77648595	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)^*(32+1)$
-73883691	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-21$	-77649387	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)^*(32+1)$
-73923245	$(-9+8^*7)^*(6*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-77649405	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)^*(32+1)$
-73925971	$(9-8^*7)^*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-77651574	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4)^*(-32-1)$
-73926065	$(9-8^*7)^*(6*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-78118927	$9-8/7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+3^*21)$
-74001149	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2-1)$	-78486588	$-9/(8/(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32)-1))$
-74001293	$-9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+2-1)$	-78774263	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(65/(4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-74106495	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2-1)$	-78774281	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(65/(4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-74224593	$-9^{\wedge}(-8+7+6)*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2+1)$	-78917586	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)*(-4/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-74354070	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^*2+1)$	-78920391	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)*(-4/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-74354266	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^*2+1)$	-79056696	$9-(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3)^*21$
-74471719	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-79056714	$-9-(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4-3)^*21$
-74471745	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-79056822	$9-(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4+3)^*21$
-74471889	$-9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-79063416	$9-(8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4-3)^*21$
-74471915	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-79063542	$9-(8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4+3)^*21$
-74579959	$9-8^{\wedge}7*(65/(4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-79953615	$(-9-8^*(7+6^*5))^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-74579977	$-9-8^{\wedge}7*(65/(4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-79997911	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$
-74707017	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5^*(4^*32-1)$	-79997929	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$
-74707187	$-9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-80000886	$9-(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$
-74707213	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*5^*(4^*32-1)$	-80001201	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6*5^*4-3)^*2-1)$
-75177613	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^*32-1)$	-80001235	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6*5^*4-3)^*2+1)$
-75177809	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^*32-1)$	-80001405	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6*5^*4+3)^*2-1)$
-75412911	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^*32+1)$	-80001439	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6*5^*4+3)^*2+1)$
-75413081	$9^*-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5/4^{\wedge}-3^*2+1)$	-80001736	$9-(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$
-75413107	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^*32+1)$	-80004711	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$
-75524559	$(9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4)^*321$	-80327655	$9^*(8+7-(65^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1)$
-75527439	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*321$	-80327673	$9^*(8+7-(65^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1)$
-75527457	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)/4^*321$	-80327925	$-9^*(8+7+(65^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1)$
-75533859	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)/4^*321$	-80327943	$-9^*(8+7+(65^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1)$
-75533877	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)/4^*321$	-80327952	$-9^*(8+7+(65^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
-75536757	$(-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)/4)^*321$	-80327970	$-9^*(8+7+(65^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1)$
-75543471	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)^*21$	-80471763	$9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))^*2+1)$
-75883311	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*5^*43)^*(2+1)$	-80471781	$9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43))^*2-1)$
-75883507	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5^*43*(2+1)$	-80471979	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)^*2+1)$
-75883572	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*43)^*(2+1)$	-80471997	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)^*2-1)$
-75883590	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*43)^*(2+1)$	-80701726	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)-21)$
-75883620	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*43)^*(2+1)$	-80703490	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)-2-1)$
-75883677	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*43/(2+1))$	-80703686	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)-2+1)$
-75883703	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*5^*43*(2+1)$	-80703735	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-75883899	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*5^*43)^*(-2-1)$	-80703833	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-76000897	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)+21)$	-80703882	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)+2-1)$
-76001611	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)-21)$	-80705842	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3)+21)$
-76201488	$-9^*8^*((7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-80708586	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3)-21)$
-76201551	$-9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-80710546	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3)-2+1)$
-76201569	$-9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-80710595	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-76201632	$-9^*8^*((7^{\wedge}6-54)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-80710693	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-80710742	$-98 * ((7^6+5) * (4+3)+2-1)$	-86471856	$-9+(8-7^6*5*(4+3))*21$
-80710938	$-98 * ((7^6+5) * (4+3)+2+1)$	-86472174	$9-(8+7^6*5*(4+3))*21$
-80712702	$-98 * ((7^6+5) * (4+3)+21)$	-86473182	$9-(8+7^6*5) * (4+3) * 21$
-80942414	$98-7^6 * (5^4+3^2 * 21)$	-86473200	$-9-(8+7^6 * 5) * (4+3) * 21$
-80942610	$-98-7^6 * (5^4+3^2 * 21)$	-86474073	$(98+7^6 * 5 * (4+3)) * -21$
-81530829	$-9 * (8+7^6 * (5-4/3) * 21)$	-86669496	$9 * 8 * (7-6/5^4-4 * 321)$
-81880215	$9-8 * (7^6-5) * (43^2+1)$	-86957316	$-9/(8/(7^6 * (5^4+32)-1))$
-81884130	$9-(8 * 7^6+5) * (43^2+1)$	-87293881	$9 * (8-(7^6-5) * 4^3 * 2) -1$
-81887175	$9-8 * (7^6+5) * (43^2+1)$	-87294023	$-9 * (8+(7^6-5) * 4^3 * 2) +1$
-82001336	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * (5+4^3 * 2) -1)$	-87294025	$-9 * (8+(7^6-5) * 4^3 * 2) -1$
-82001370	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * (5+4^3 * 2) +1)$	-88938369	$-9 * (8+((7^6-5) * 4-3) * 21)$
-82574909	$9 * (8+7 * (6-5 * 4^3 * 2) +1)$	-88939359	$9 * (8-((7^6-5) * 4+3) * 21)$
-82574911	$9 * (8+7 * (6-5 * 4^3 * 2) -1)$	-88939503	$-9 * (8+((7^6-5) * 4+3) * 21)$
-82575053	$-9 * (8-7 * (6-5 * 4^3 * 2) +1)$	-88945929	$-9 * (8+((7^6+5) * 4-3) * 21)$
-82575055	$-9 * (8-7 * (6-5 * 4^3 * 2) -1)$	-88947063	$-9 * (8+((7^6+5) * 4+3) * 21)$
-82575667	$9 * (8-7 * (6+5 * 4^3 * 2) -1)$	-89128611	$9+(8-76) * 5 * (4^3 * 2 -1)$
-82575809	$-9 * (8+7 * (6+5 * 4^3 * 2) +1)$	-89128883	$9+(8-76) * (5 * 4^3 * 2 -1)$
-82575811	$-9 * (8+7 * (6+5 * 4^3 * 2) -1)$	-89129019	$9+(8-76) * (5 * 4^3 * 2 +1)$
-82589526	$9 * (8-7^6 * (54+3+21))$	-89129291	$9+(8-76) * 5 * (4^3 * 2 +1)$
-82589670	$-9 * (8+7^6 * (54+3+21))$	-89413069	$(9-8/7^6-6 * 5) * (4 * (3+2) -1)$
-82727649	$9 * 8 * (7^6 * 5 - 5^4 - 4^3 + 2) -1$	-89413411	$(9+8/7^6-6 * 5) * (-4 * (3+2) +1)$
-82955358	$9 * 8 - 7^6 * (54-3) * 21$	-89997588	$9 * (8-(7^6-5) * (4^3+21))$
-83338024	$-9 * 8 * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 * 2 -1)$	-89997732	$-9 * (8+(7^6-5) * (43^2-1))$
-83338220	$-9 * 8 * (7^6 * 5 + 4^3 * 2 +1)$	-90000856	$(-9-8) * ((7^6 * 5 - 4) * 3^2 -1)$
-84108739	$(9 * 8 - 7^6 * 5) * ((4^3)^2 -1)$	-90000890	$(-9-8) * ((7^6 * 5 - 4) * 3^2 +1)$
-84118937	$98-7^6 * 5 * ((4^3)^2 -1)$	-90001413	$9 * (8-7^6 * (54+32-1))$
-84118963	$9 * 8 - 7^6 * 5 * ((4^3)^2 -1)$	-90001468	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - (4+3+2) +1)$
-84119133	$-98-7^6 * 5 * ((4^3)^2 -1)$	-90001502	$(9+8) * (7^6 * 5 - (4+3+2) -1)$
-84381021	$-9 * 8 * (7/(6/5/4-3))^2 +1$	-90001557	$-9 * (8+7^6 * (54+32-1))$
-84589533	$98-7^6 * (5 * (4^3)^2 -1)$	-90002080	$(-9-8) * ((7^6 * 5 + 4) * 3^2 -1)$
-84589559	$9 * 8 - 7^6 * (5 * (4^3)^2 -1)$	-90002114	$(-9-8) * ((7^6 * 5 + 4) * 3^2 +1)$
-84589703	$9 * 8 - 7^6 * (5/(4^3)^2 -1)$	-90005238	$9 * (8-(7^6+5) * (4^3+21))$
-84589729	$-98-7^6 * (5 * (4^3)^2 -1)$	-90005382	$-9 * (8+(7^6+5) * (43^2-1))$
-84602444	$9 * 8 - 7^6 * (543^2 -1)$	-90350583	$9-8 * (7^6-5) * 4 * (3+21)$
-84706649	$9 * (8 * (7^6 * 5 - 5 + 4) + 3) * 2 + 1$	-90350601	$-9-8 * (7^6-5) * 4 * (3+21)$
-84706651	$9 * (8 * (7^6 * 5 - 5 + 4) + 3) * 2 - 1$	-90353943	$9-(8 * 7^6-5) * 4 * (3+21)$
-84706695	$9 * 8 * (7^6 * 5 - 4) * (3-21)$	-90354903	$9-(8 * 7^6+5) * 4 * (3+21)$
-84706757	$9 * (8 * (7^6 * 5 - 5 + 4) - 3) * 2 + 1$	-90358263	$9-8 * (7^6+5) * 4 * (3+21)$
-84706759	$9 * (8 * (7^6 * 5 - 5 + 4) - 3) * 2 - 1$	-90437610	$(9+8 * 7^6) * (5-4^3 * 2 +1)$
-84707801	$9 * (-8 * (7^6 * 5 + 4) + 3) * 2 + 1$	-90441060	$(-9-8 * 7^6) * (5+4^3 * 2 -1)$
-84707803	$9 * (-8 * (7^6 * 5 + 4) + 3) * 2 - 1$	-90441750	$(-9-8 * 7^6) * (5+4^3 * 2 +1)$
-84707847	$9 * 8 * (7^6 * 5 + 4) * (3-21)$	-90687529	$(-9/(8+(7+6)^(5-4+3)))^2)^{-1}$
-84707909	$9 * (-8 * (7^6 * 5 + 4) - 3) * 2 + 1$	-91056303	$9 * ((8-(7^6-5) * 43) * 2 + 1)$
-84707911	$9 * (-8 * (7^6 * 5 + 4) - 3) * 2 - 1$	-91056321	$9 * ((8-(7^6-5) * 43) * 2 - 1)$
-84824831	$98-7^6 * (5 * (4^3)^2 + 1)$	-91056375	$9 * (8-(7^6-5) * 43^2 + 1)$
-84824857	$9 * 8 - 7^6 * (5 * (4^3)^2 + 1)$	-91056519	$-9 * (8+(7^6-5) * 43^2 - 1)$
-84825001	$9 * 8 - 7^6 * (5/(4^3)^2 - 1)$	-91056537	$-9 * (8+(7^6-5) * 43^2 + 1)$
-84825027	$-98-7^6 * (5 * (4^3)^2 + 1)$	-91056591	$-9 * ((8+(7^6-5) * 43) * 2 - 1)$
-84837742	$9 * 8 - 7^6 * (543^2 + 1)$	-91060245	$9 * (8-7^6 * (54+32) + 1)$
-84945267	$9 * (8-(7^6-5)/4) * 321$	-91060263	$9 * (8-7^6 * (54+32) - 1)$
-84968307	$9 * (8-(7^6-5)/4) * 321$	-91060389	$-9 * (8+7^6 * (54+32) - 1)$
-84968451	$-9 * (8+(7^6-5)/4) * 321$	-91060407	$-9 * (8+7^6 * (54+32) + 1)$
-84991491	$-9 * (8+(7^6-5)/4) * 321$	-91064043	$9 * ((8-(7^6+5) * 43) * 2 + 1)$
-85285085	$(9 * 8 - 7^6 * 5) * ((4^3)^2 + 1)$	-91064061	$9 * ((8-(7^6+5) * 43) * 2 - 1)$
-85295427	$98-7^6 * 5 * ((4^3)^2 + 1)$	-91064259	$-9 * (8+(7^6+5) * 43^2 - 1)$
-85295453	$9 * 8 - 7^6 * 5 * ((4^3)^2 + 1)$	-91064277	$-9 * (8+(7^6+5) * 43^2 + 1)$
-85295623	$-98-7^6 * 5 * ((4^3)^2 + 1)$	-91295615	$9-8 * 7^6 * ((5+43) * 2 + 1)$
-85719126	$(-9+8 * 7^6) * (5-4^3 * 2 + 1)$	-91796922	$(9-8 * 7) * ((6-5+4) * 3^2 + 1)$
-85719780	$(-9+8 * 7^6) * (5-4^3 * 2 - 1)$	-92001501	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * (5 * 4 + 3) * 2 - 1)$
-85722396	$(9-8 * 7^6) * (5+4^3 * 2 - 1)$	-92001535	$(-9-8) * (7^6 * (5 * 4 + 3) * 2 + 1)$
-85723050	$(9-8 * 7^6) * (5+4^3 * 2 + 1)$	-92012273	$9 * ((-8^7+6) * 5 + 4^3 * 2) + 1$
-85766076	$9 * ((8-7^6 * 54^3)/2 + 1)$	-92115180	$9 * (8-(7^6-5) * (43^2+1))$
-85766238	$-9 * ((8+7^6 * 54) * 3/2 + 1)$	-92115324	$-9 * (8+(7^6-5) * (43^2+1))$
-85997407	$(-9-8) * ((7^6-5) * 43-21)$	-92119095	$9 * (8-7^6 * (54+32+1))$
-85998121	$(-9-8) * ((7^6-5) * 43+21)$	-92119239	$-9 * (8+7^6 * (54+32+1))$
-86004717	$(-9-8) * ((7^6+5) * 43-21)$	-92123010	$9 * (8-(7^6+5) * (43^2+1))$
-86005431	$(-9-8) * ((7^6+5) * 43+21)$	-92123154	$-9 * (8+(7^6+5) * (43^2+1))$
-86328108	$(9+8) * ((-7-6) * 5^4 * (3/2) + 1)$	-92157111	$-9 * ((8^8(-7/6)/5)^{-4-3-321})$
-86328142	$(-9-8) * ((7+6) * 5^4 * (3/2) + 1)$	-92159433	$-9 * ((8^8(-7/6)/5)^{-4-3-321})$
-86469957	$(98-7^6 * 5 * (4+3)) * 21$	-92159679	$-9 * (8^8(-7/6)/5)^{-4-4+321}$
-86470830	$9+(8-7^6 * 5) * (4+3) * 21$	-92160321	$-9 * (8^8(-7/6)/5)^{-4-4-321}$
-86471838	$9+(8-7^6 * 5 * (4+3)) * 21$	-92160567	$-9 * ((8^8(-7/6)/5)^{-4+3 * 21})$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-92162889	$-9 * ((8^{(-7/6)}/5)^{-4+321})$	-98826345	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4 + 3) * 21$
-92232798	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 * 32 - 1)$	-98832195	$(9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 43)) * 21$
-92232994	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5) / 4 * 32 + 1)$	-98832573	$(-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 43)) * 21$
-92240638	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) / 4 * 32 - 1)$	-98835903	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21$
-92240834	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge}6 + 5) / 4 * 32 + 1)$	-98835921	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21$
-93238371	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76 * 54^{\wedge}3) * (-2 - 1)$	-99088471	$9 * (8 + 7 * 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3 / 2)) - 1$
-93297420	$-9^{\wedge}8 * (7/6 + (5+4)^{-3/2+1})$	-99088613	$-9 * (8 - 7 * 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3 / 2)) + 1$
-93585051	$(98 - 7 * 65) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 - 1)$	-99088615	$-9 * (8 - 7 * 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge}3 / 2)) - 1$
-93585765	$(98 - 7 * 65) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 + 1)$	-99092249	$9 * (8 - 7 * 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3 / 2)) + 1$
-93882390	$(9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43)) * 21$	-99092251	$9 * (8 - 7 * 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3 / 2)) - 1$
-93883545	$(9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43)) * 21$	-99092393	$-9 * (8 + 7 * 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3 / 2)) + 1$
-93883725	$9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43)) * 21$	-99092395	$-9 * (8 + 7 * 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge}3 / 2)) - 1$
-93883743	$-9 + (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43)) * 21$	-100001633	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4 * 3 - 2) - 1)$
-93883830	$9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43) * 21$	-100001667	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4 * 3 - 2) + 1)$
-93883881	$(9 - 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43)) * 21$	-100617108	$(9 - (8 + 7)^{\wedge}6) * (5 + 4 - (3 * 2)^{\wedge} - 1)$
-93883885	$9 + 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43) * 21$	-100617267	$(9 + (8 + 7)^{\wedge}6) * (-5 - 4 + (3 * 2)^{\wedge} - 1)$
-93883901	$9 - 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43) * 21$	-100710000	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 21)$
-93883903	$-9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43) * 21$	-1011178123	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * 43 / 2 - 1)$
-93883919	$-9 - 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43) * 21$	-101178139	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * 43 / 2 + 1)$
-93883923	$(-9 + 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43)) * 21$	-101449539	$-9 * (8^{\wedge}(7 - 6 + 5) * 43 - 21)$
-93883974	$-9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43) * 21$	-101449701	$-9 * (8^{\wedge}(7 - 6 + 5) * 43 - 2 - 1)$
-93884061	$9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43)) * 21$	-101449755	$-9 * (8^{\wedge}(7 - 6 + 5) * 43 + 2 + 1)$
-93884079	$-9 - (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43)) * 21$	-101449917	$-9 * (8^{\wedge}(7 - 6 + 5) * 43 + 21)$
-93884259	$(-9 - 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43)) * 21$	-101644173	$(9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4) * 3^{\wedge}(2 + 1)$
-93885414	$(-9 * 8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 - 43)) * 21$	-101644397	$9 * (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4 * -3 + 2) + 1$
-94187025	$(-9 / ((8 + 7) * (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 - 3)))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge} - 1$	-101644399	$9 * (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4 * -3 + 2) - 1$
-94366359	$9 * (8 * (76 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 / 2) + 1)$	-101644433	$-9 * (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4 * 3 + 2) + 1$
-94366377	$9 * (8 * (76 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 / 2) - 1)$	-101644435	$-9 * (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4 * 3 + 2) - 1$
-94368815	$9 * 8 * (7 * 6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 / 2) + 1$	-101644659	$(-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4) * 3^{\wedge}(2 + 1)$
-94368817	$9 * 8 * (7 * 6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 / 2) - 1$	-101647953	$(9 - (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4) * 3^{\wedge}(2 + 1)$
-94374863	$-9 * 8 * (7 * 6 + 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 / 2) + 1$	-101648439	$(9 + (8 / 7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * 4) * -3^{\wedge}(2 + 1)$
-94374865	$-9 * 8 * (7 * 6 + 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 / 2) - 1$	-101648687	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 54 - 3) * 2 + 1)$
-94497841	$(-9 / ((8 + 7) * 6^{\wedge}5 / 4 + 3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge} - 1$	-101648783	$9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 54 + 3) * 2 + 1)$
-94770225	$(-9 / ((8 + 7) * (6^{\wedge}5 / 4 + 3)))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge} - 1$	-101648785	$-9 - 8 * ((7^{\wedge}6 * 54 + 3) * 2 - 1)$
-95295114	$9 * (-8 + (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4) * (3 - 21))$	-101649033	$(9 - (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4) * 3^{\wedge}(2 + 1)$
-95659359	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 * 6 / 54 - 3) + 21$	-101649519	$(9 + (8 / 7^{\wedge}6 - 6 + 5) * 4) * -3^{\wedge}(2 + 1)$
-95659401	$9^{\wedge}8 * (7 * 6 / 54 - 3) - 21$	-101652813	$(9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4) * 3^{\wedge}(2 + 1)$
-96001227	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 43) - 21)$	-101653037	$9 * (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 * -3 + 2) + 1$
-96001941	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 43) + 21)$	-101653039	$9 * (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 * -3 + 2) - 1$
-96206481	$(9 - 8 * (7 * 6 + 5)) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 - 1)$	-101653073	$-9 * (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 * 3 + 2) + 1$
-96207215	$(9 - 8 * (7 * 6 + 5)) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 + 1)$	-101653075	$-9 * (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4 * 3 + 2) - 1$
-96354433	$98 - 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * ((4^{\wedge}3) / 2 - 1)$	-101653299	$(-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) * 4) * 3^{\wedge}(2 + 1)$
-96354594	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 43 * 2) - 1)$	-101711475	$9 - (8 + 76 * 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 - 1)$
-96354612	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 43 * 2) + 1)$	-101712251	$9 - (8 + 76 * 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 + 1)$
-96472171	$9 - 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (43 / 2 - 1)$	-101821664	$(-9 / ((8 * 7 + 6)^{\wedge}5 + 4^{\wedge}3 / 2))^{\wedge} - 1$
-96730865	$9 * ((-8^{\wedge}7 + 6) * 5 - 4^{\wedge}3 / 2) + 1$	-102001326	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge}6 * (54 - 3) - 21)$
-96730867	$9 * ((-8^{\wedge}7 + 6) * 5 - 4^{\wedge}3 / 2) - 1$	-102119323	$9 - 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 * 43 / 2 + 1)$
-96731405	$-9 * ((8^{\wedge}7 + 6) * 5 + 4^{\wedge}3 / 2) + 1$	-102119332	$-98 * 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4 - 3 / 21)$
-97517187	$9 + (8 - 76 * 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 - 1)$	-102161250	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 21)$
-97517931	$9 + (8 - 76 * 5) * (4^{\wedge}3 / 2 + 1)$	-102330000	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * (32 + 1))$
-97779132	$9^{\wedge}8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (54 + 3) * 21$	-102331917	$9^{\wedge}8 - (8 + 7 + 6) * (-5 - (4 * 3)^{\wedge}(2 + 1))$
-98814399	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4^{\wedge}3) * 21$	-102335616	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 2 - 1)$
-98814417	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4^{\wedge}3) * 21$	-102335634	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 2 + 1)$
-98817747	$(9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 43)) * 21$	-102341250	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * (32 - 1))$
-98818125	$(-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 43)) * 21$	-102380625	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * (3 + 21))$
-98823975	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4 - 3) * 21$	-102396933	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}4 + 3) * 21)$
-98824416	$9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4) - 3) * 21$	-102398067	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21)$
-98824542	$9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4) + 3) * 21$	-102414375	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * (3 - 21))$
-98824927	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4 / 3) * 21$	-102498287	$(9 + 8) * ((7 - 6 * 5) * 4^{\wedge}3 / 2 + 1)$
-98824945	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4 / 3) * 21$	-102498561	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 21)$
-98824983	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4 + 3) * 21$	-102513125	$-9 * (8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * (3 + 2 - 1)$
-98825123	$9 - (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 - 4 / 3) * 21$	-102513561	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 21)$
-98825133	$(9 - 8 / 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4 + 3)) * (2 + 1)$	-102513939	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 / 3 + 21)$
-98825179	$9 - (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4 / 3) * 21$	-102517311	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 / 3 - 21)$
-98825187	$(-9 - 8 / 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 * (4 + 3)) * (2 + 1)$	-102517689	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 / 3 + 21)$
-98825319	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4 - 3) * 21$	-102518125	$-9 * (8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * (3 + 2 - 1)$
-98825375	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4 / 3) * 21$	-102532689	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 21)$
-98825403	$9 - (8 / 7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4 * 3) * 21$	-102616875	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * (3 - 21))$
-98825760	$9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4) - 3) * 21$	-102633183	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 + (5^{\wedge}4 - 3) * 21)$
-98825778	$9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4) - 3) * 21$	-102634317	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 21)$
-98825886	$9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4) + 3) * 21$	-102650625	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * (3 + 21))$
-98826327	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 * 5 + 4 + 3) * 21$	-102690000	$-9 * ((8 + 7)^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4^{\wedge}3 * (32 - 1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-102695616	$-9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*32-1)$	-104317570	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-102695634	$-9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*32+1)$	-104317766	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-102701250	$-9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*(32+1))$	-104321250	$-9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*321)$
-102707505	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*((5+43)^*2+1))$	-104576888	$(9/(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-102707649	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*((5+43)^*2+1))$	-104576890	$(-9/(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4)^{\wedge}3+2))^{\wedge}-1$
-102870000	$-9^*((8+7)^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4*3*21)$	-104602774	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2-1)$
-103049253	$9^{\wedge}8*((-76/54)^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	-104603034	$(-9/(8+7^{\wedge}6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3+2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-103190986	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2-1)$	-104838072	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)^*2+1)$
-103215070	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-106167900	$9-(87-6)^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-103215266	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-106168230	$9-(87-6)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-103426284	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)^*2+1)$	-106168248	$-9-(87-6)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-103653000	$-9^*8/(7/(6^{\wedge}(5+4)-321))$	-106168392	$9-(87-6)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-103718692	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-106168716	$9-(87-6)^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-103718888	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-106168734	$-9-(87-6)^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-103748680	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^*4)*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-106232175	$(9+8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43)^*21$
-103748876	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^*4)*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-106232355	$9+(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43)^*21$
-103758382	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-106232373	$-9+(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43)^*21$
-103758578	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-106232511	$(9-8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43)^*21$
-103760244	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3*21)$	-106232553	$(9-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43)^*-21$
-103761910	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3+2)-1)$	-106232691	$9-(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43)^*21$
-103762106	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+3+2)+1)$	-106232709	$-9-(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43)^*21$
-103763184	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-32-1)$	-106232889	$(9+8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43)^*-21$
-103763281	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-32)+1$	-106241205	$(9+8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43)^*21$
-103763282	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-32)^{\wedge}1$	-106241385	$9+(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43)^*21$
-103763283	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-32)-1$	-106241403	$-9+(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43)^*21$
-103763380	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-32+1)$	-106241541	$(9-8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43)^*21$
-103763772	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-106241583	$(9-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43)^*-21$
-103764066	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3-21)$	-106241721	$9-(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43)^*21$
-103764654	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3-21)$	-106241739	$-9-(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43)^*21$
-103765438	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-106241919	$(9+8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43)^*-21$
-103765634	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-106288199	$9^{\wedge}8*(-76/54/3-2)+1$
-103765732	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3*2-1)$	-106288201	$9^{\wedge}8*(-76/54/3-2)-1$
-103766026	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3-2+1)$	-107426350	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4*321)$
-103766075	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-107543999	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
-103766103	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)+21$	-107616677	$((9^{\wedge}8-7^*6)^*-5+43)/2-1$
-103766145	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3)-21$	-107616718	$((9^{\wedge}8-7^*6)^*-5-43)/2+1$
-103766173	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3/2-1)$	-107616887	$((9^{\wedge}8+7^*6)^*-5+43)/2-1$
-103766222	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3+2-1)$	-107616928	$((9^{\wedge}8+7^*6)^*-5-43)/2+1$
-103766345	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3)^*2)+1$	-108000711	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3*21)$
-103766347	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3)^*2)-1$	-108001221	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-32-1)$
-103766369	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3/2+1)$	-108001237	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-32)+1$
-103766467	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3/2-1)$	-108001238	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-32)^{\wedge}1$
-103766489	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3)^*2)+1$	-108001239	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-32)-1$
-103766491	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}(6-5+4+3)^*2)-1$	-108001255	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-32+1)$
-103766614	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3-2+1)$	-108001374	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3-21)$
-103766663	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3/2+1)$	-108001476	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3-21)$
-103766691	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)+21$	-108001647	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*2-1)$
-103766733	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3)-21$	-108001752	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3)-21$
-103766761	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-108001812	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3)+21$
-103766810	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3+2-1)$	-108001863	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)^*2+1)$
-103767104	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3*2+1)$	-108002088	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3+21)$
-103767202	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-108002190	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3+21)$
-103767398	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-108002309	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+32-1)$
-103768182	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)-3+21)$	-108002325	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+32)+1$
-103768770	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3+21)$	-108002326	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+32)^{\wedge}1$
-103769064	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-108002327	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+32)-1$
-103769456	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+32-1)$	-108002343	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+32+1)$
-103769553	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+32)+1$	-108002853	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3*21)$
-103769554	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+32)^{\wedge}1$	-108008175	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4*321$
-103769555	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+32)-1$	-108021015	$9^{\wedge}8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4*321$
-103769652	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+32+1)$	-108125864	$-9/8^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)/(4*3))^{\wedge}2-1)$
-103770730	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3+2)-1)$	-108236873	$(-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-103770926	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+3+2)+1)$	-108237287	$(9+8*7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-103772592	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)+3*21)$	-108602840	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4*321)$
-103774258	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-109426383	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*54*(3+21)$
-103774454	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-110097645	$(9-8^{\wedge}7/6)^*((5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1)$
-103783960	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^*4)*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-110099913	$(9-8^{\wedge}7/(6/5))^*(4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
-103784156	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^*4)*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-110100051	$9-(8+76)^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-103813948	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+54)*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-110100387	$9-(8+76)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-103814144	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+54)*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-110100555	$9-(8+76)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-104119293	$9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4/3-21))$	-110100891	$9-(8+76)^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-104119437	$9^*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4/3-21))$	-110101047	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7/(6/5))^*(4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-110103315	$(-9 \cdot 8^{7/6}) * ((5^{4+3})/2+1)$	-113279959	$-9 * (8^{7*6+5^{4*3*2}}) - 1$
-110109288	$(9 - (8+7)^6) * (5^4/3+2+1)$	-113347458	$9 * (-8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * (3-21))$
-110109462	$(-9 - (8+7)^6) * (5^4/3+2+1)$	-113363766	$-9 * (8^{7*6+(5^{4-3})} * 21)$
-110156203	$(9 - 8^{*7}) * (6^{*5^{4^4}}(3/2) - 1)$	-113364900	$-9 * (8^{7*6+(5^{4+3})} * 21)$
-110156297	$(9 - 8^{*7}) * (6^{*5^{4^4}}(3/2) + 1)$	-113381208	$-9 * (8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * (3+21))$
-110343175	$(-9 - 8) / (7 / ((6^{*5+4})^{(3+2)} + 1))$	-113420583	$-9 * (8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * (32-1))$
-110657826	$-9^{(8+7+6)} * (5^{4*3-2+1})$	-113426199	$-9 * (8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * 32-1)$
-110775924	$-9^{(8+7+6)} * (5^{4*3+2-1})$	-113426217	$-9 * (8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * 32+1)$
-110886839	$9 * (8 - (7^{*6+5})^{*4^3} + 2) + 1$	-113431833	$-9 * (8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * (32+1))$
-110886841	$9 * (8 - (7^{*6+5})^{*4^3} - 2) - 1$	-113446833	$-9 * 8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} - 321$
-110886983	$-9 * (8 + (7^{*6+5})^{*4^3} + 2) + 1$	-113508343	$9 - 8^{(7-6+5)} * (432+1)$
-110886985	$-9 * (8 + (7^{*6+5})^{*4^3} - 2) - 1$	-113508361	$-9 - 8^{(7-6+5)} * (432+1)$
-110894022	$-9^{(8+7+6)} * (5^{4*3+2+1})$	-114001524	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{4*6} * (54+3) - 21)$
-111111112	$(-9 - (8 + (7 - 6 + 5 + 4)^{4^3}))^{4^3} - 1$	-114001864	$(9+8) * (7^{4*6} * (5 - 4^{3+2}) + 1)$
-111166137	$9 * (8 - (7^{4*6} * 5 - 4^3) * 21)$	-114001898	$(9+8) * (7^{4*6} * (5 - 4^{3+2}) - 1)$
-111166281	$-9 * (8 + (7^{4*6} * 5 - 4^3) * 21)$	-114002238	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{4*6} * (54+3) + 21)$
-111168666	$9 * (8 - 7^{4*6} * 5 + 43) * 21$	-114031674	$9 + 87 * (6 - 5 * (4^{3+2} - 1))$
-111170106	$9 * (8 - (7^{4*6} * 5 - 43) * 21)$	-114031692	$-9 + 87 * (6 - 5 * (4^{3+2} - 1))$
-111170250	$-9 * (8 + (7^{4*6} * 5 - 43) * 21)$	-114032022	$9 + 87 * (6 - 5 * 4^{3+2} + 1)$
-111171690	$-9 * (8 + 7^{4*6} * 5 - 43) * 21$	-114032196	$9 + 87 * (6 - 5 * 4^{3+2} - 1)$
-111177054	$-9 * (8 + (7^{4*6} * 5 - 4 - 3) * 21)$	-114032544	$9 + 87 * (6 - 5 * (4^{3+2} + 1))$
-111177981	$9 * (8 - (7^{4*6} * 5 - 4/3) * 21)$	-114032562	$-9 + 87 * (6 - 5 * (4^{3+2} + 1))$
-111178125	$-9 * (8 + (7^{4*6} * 5 - 4/3) * 21)$	-114032718	$9 - 87 * (6 + 5 * (4^{3+2} - 1))$
-111178188	$-9 * (8 + (7^{4*6} * 5 - 4 + 3) * 21)$	-114033066	$9 - 87 * (6 + 5 * 4^{3+2} - 1)$
-111178566	$-9 * (8 + (7^{4*6} * 5 + 4 - 3) * 21)$	-114033240	$9 - 87 * (6 + 5 * 4^{3+2} + 1)$
-111178629	$-9 * (8 + (7^{4*6} * 5 + 4/3) * 21)$	-114033588	$9 - 87 * (6 + 5 * (4^{3+2} + 1))$
-111179556	$9 * (8 - (7^{4*6} * 5 + 4 + 3) * 21)$	-114353532	$(-9 * 8 + 7^{4*6} * 54) * (3 - 21)$
-111179700	$-9 * (8 + (7^{4*6} * 5 + 4 + 3) * 21)$	-114354522	$(-9 - 8 + 7^{4*6} * 54) * (3 - 21)$
-111184920	$9 * (8 - 7^{4*6} * 5 - 43) * 21$	-114354621	$9 * ((8 - 7^{4*6} * 54 + 3) * 2 + 1)$
-111186360	$9 * (8 - (7^{4*6} * 5 + 43) * 21)$	-114354675	$9 - (8 - 7^{4*6} * 54) * (3 - 21)$
-111186504	$-9 * (8 + (7^{4*6} * 5 + 43) * 21)$	-114354729	$9 * ((8 - 7^{4*6} * 54 - 3) * 2 + 1)$
-111187944	$-9 * (8 + 7^{4*6} * 5 + 43) * 21$	-114354747	$9 * ((8 - 7^{4*6} * 54 - 3) * 2 - 1)$
-111190329	$9 * (8 - (7^{4*6} * 5 + 4 + 3) * 21)$	-114354801	$9 * (8 - (7^{4*6} * 54 + 3) * 2 + 1)$
-111190473	$-9 * (8 + (7^{4*6} * 5 + 4 + 3) * 21)$	-114354855	$-9 * (8 + (7^{4*6} * 54 - 3) * 2 + 1)$
-111295882	$9 * 8 - 7^{4*6} * (5^{4+3} + 321)$	-114354945	$-9 * (8 + (7^{4*6} * 54 + 3) * 2 - 1)$
-111295937	$9 + 8 - 7^{4*6} * (5^{4+3} + 321)$	-114354963	$9 + (8 + 7^{4*6} * 54) * (3 - 21)$
-111295953	$9 - 8 - 7^{4*6} * (5^{4+3} + 321)$	-114354981	$-9 + (8 + 7^{4*6} * 54) * (3 - 21)$
-111295955	$-9 - 8 - 7^{4*6} * (5^{4+3} + 321)$	-114355134	$(9 + 8 + 7^{4*6} * 54) * (3 - 21)$
-111295971	$-9 - 8 - 7^{4*6} * (5^{4+3} + 321)$	-114356124	$(9 * 8 + 7^{4*6} * 54) * (3 - 21)$
-111296026	$-9 * 8 - 7^{4*6} * (5^{4+3} + 321)$	-115051833	$-9 * (8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * 321)$
-111440583	$9 * (-8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * 321)$	-115283378	$-98 * ((7^{4*6} * 5 - 4^3) * 2 - 1)$
-112941477	$(9 + (8 - 7^{4*6} * 5) * 4^3) * (2 + 1)$	-115283574	$-98 * ((7^{4*6} * 5 - 4^3) * 2 + 1)$
-112941531	$(-9 + (8 - 7^{4*6} * 5) * 4^3) * (2 + 1)$	-115287494	$-98 * ((7^{4*6} * 5 - 43) * 2 - 1)$
-112942263	$9 - 8 * (7^{4*6} * 5 - 4) * (3 + 21)$	-115287690	$-98 * ((7^{4*6} * 5 - 43) * 2 + 1)$
-112942935	$9 - (8 * 7^{4*6} * 5 - 4) * (3 + 21)$	-115291022	$-98 * ((7^{4*6} * 5) * (4 * 3 - 2) - 1)$
-112942942	$98 - 7^{4*6} * 5 * 4^3 * (2 + 1)$	-115304350	$-98 * ((7^{4*6} * 5 + 43) * 2 - 1)$
-112943127	$9 - (8 * 7^{4*6} * 5 + 4) * (3 + 21)$	-115304546	$-98 * ((7^{4*6} * 5 + 43) * 2 + 1)$
-112943138	$-98 - 7^{4*6} * 5 * 4^3 * (2 + 1)$	-115308466	$-98 * ((7^{4*6} * 5 + 4^3) * 2 - 1)$
-112943799	$9 - 8 * (7^{4*6} * 5 + 4) * (3 + 21)$	-115308662	$-98 * ((7^{4*6} * 5 + 4^3) * 2 + 1)$
-112943817	$-9 - 8 * (7^{4*6} * 5 + 4) * (3 + 21)$	-115371881	$(9/8 - 7/6) * (-5/4 - 3/2 - 1)$
-112944549	$(9 - (8 + 7^{4*6} * 5) * 4^3) * (2 + 1)$	-115676991	$9/8 * (7 - 6 - 5 * (4^3)^2 + 1)$
-112944603	$(9 + (8 + 7^{4*6} * 5) * 4^3) * (-2 - 1)$	-116001897	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{4*6} * (5 * 4^3 - 2) - 1)$
-112984055	$9 - 8^{(7-6+5)} * (432-1)$	-116001931	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{4*6} * (5 * 4^3 - 2) + 1)$
-112984073	$-9 - 8^{(7-6+5)} * (432-1)$	-116472582	$-9 * (8 + 7^{4*6} * 5 * (43 - 21))$
-113045583	$-9 * 8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * 321$	-116702839	$9 - 8 * (7^{4*6} - 5) * 4 * (32 - 1)$
-113060583	$9 * (-8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * (32+1))$	-116708419	$9 - (8 * 7^{4*6} + 5) * 4 * (32 - 1)$
-113066199	$9 * (-8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * 32+1)$	-116712759	$9 - 8 * (7^{4*6} + 5) * 4 * (32 - 1)$
-113066217	$9 * (-8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * 32-1)$	-116920468	$98 * (7^{4*6} - 5 * (4^3 + 2 - 1))$
-113071833	$9 * (-8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * (32-1))$	-116920860	$98 * (7^{4*6} - 5 * 4^3 + 2 + 1)$
-113111208	$9 * (-8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * (3+21))$	-116921056	$98 * (7^{4*6} - 5 * 4^3 + 2 - 1)$
-113127516	$9 * (-8^{7*6+(5^{4+3})} * 21)$	-116921448	$98 * (7^{4*6} - 5 * (4^3 + 2 + 1))$
-113128650	$9 * (-8^{7*6+(5^{4-3})} * 21)$	-117177912	$9 + (8 - 7^{65}) * (4^3 + 2 - 1)$
-113144958	$-9 * (8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * (3-21))$	-117178806	$9 + (8 - 7^{65}) * (4^3 + 2 + 1)$
-113212457	$-9 * (8^{7*6-5^{4*3}} * 2) + 1$	-117648775	$(9 - 8/7 - 6/5) * (4 * 3^2 + 1)$
-113212459	$-9 * (8^{7*6-5^{4*3}} * 2) - 1$	-117649225	$(9 + 8 * 7^{4*6} * 5) * (4 * 3^2 - 1)$
-113229144	$9 * (8^{7*6-5^{4*3}} * 3 + 21)$	-118001896	$(9 + 8) * (7^{4*6} * (5 - 4^3) + 2 + 1)$
-113244144	$9 * (-8^{7*6+5^{4/3}} + 21)$	-118001930	$(9 + 8) * (7^{4*6} * (5 - 4^3) + 2 - 1)$
-113244522	$9 * (-8^{7*6+5^{4/3}} - 21)$	-118001964	$(9 + 8) * (7^{4*6} * (5 - 4^3) - 2 + 1)$
-113247894	$-9 * (8^{7*6+5^{4/3}} - 21)$	-118001998	$(9 + 8) * (7^{4*6} * (5 - 4^3) - 2 - 1)$
-113248272	$-9 * (8^{7*6+5^{4/3}} + 21)$	-118237173	$9 * (8 - 7^{4*6} * 5 * (4/3 + 21))$
-113263272	$-9 * (8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} + 21)$	-118237317	$-9 * (8 + 7^{4*6} * 5 * (4/3 + 21))$
-113279957	$-9 * (8^{7*6+5^{4*3}} * 2) + 1$	-118588680	$(9 * 8 - 7^{4*6} * (5 + 43)) * 21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-118589835	$(9+8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*21$	-124518495	$(9-8*(7+6))*(5^*4\wedge 3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-118590015	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*21$	-126000567	$(9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*21$
-118590033	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*21$	-126001722	$(9+8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*21$
-118590171	$(9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*21$	-126001902	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*21$
-118590175	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*21$	-126001920	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*21$
-118590209	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*21$	-126002058	$(9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*21$
-118590213	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*-21$	-126002100	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*-21$
-118590351	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*21$	-126002238	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*21$
-118590369	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*21$	-126002256	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*21$
-118590549	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*-21$	-126002436	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*-21$
-118591704	$(9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+43))^*-21$	-126003591	$(9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(54-3))^*-21$
-119274967	$98-7^*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-126660105	$9^{\wedge}8*(7^*6/(5+4)^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-119275163	$-98-7^*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-126825524	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(-5^*4+3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-119275415	$98-7^*(65^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-126825720	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(-5^*4+3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-119275625	$-98-7^*(65^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-127059975	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*-5+4)+3)^*(2+1)$
-119275877	$98-7^*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-127060037	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*-5+4))^*3+2+1$
-119276073	$-98-7^*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-127060039	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*-5+4))^*3+2-1$
-119531375	$9+8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5-4*(32+1))$	-127060073	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*-5+4))^*3-2+1$
-119766610	$9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(32+1)+1)$	-127060075	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*-5+4))^*3-2-1$
-119766754	$-9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(32+1)+1)$	-127060137	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*-5+4)-3)^*(2+1)$
-120001827	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4-3)^*(2+1)$	-127060299	$(-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4))^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-120001908	$9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(32+1)-1)$	-127060847	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3^*2)+1$
-120001929	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3-2-1)$	-127060849	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3^*2)-1$
-120001945	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3-2)+1$	-127060991	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3^*2)+1$
-120001946	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3-2/1)$	-127060993	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3^*2)-1$
-120001947	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3-2)-1$	-127061541	$(9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4))^*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-120002013	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3+2)+1$	-127061703	$9*(-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)+3)^*(2+1)$
-120002014	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3+2/1)$	-127061765	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4))^*3-2+1$
-120002015	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3+2)-1$	-127061767	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4))^*3-2-1$
-120002031	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3-2-1)$	-127061801	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4))^*3+2+1$
-120002052	$-9^*8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}(32+1)-1)$	-127061803	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4))^*3+2-1$
-120002133	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4+3)^*(2+1)$	-127061865	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4))^*3*(2+1)$
-120707721	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))^*2+1)$	-127087953	$9^{\wedge}8*7-65^{\wedge}4*(3+21)$
-120707739	$-9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))^*2-1$	-127734048	$(9-8^*7^*6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-120707793	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))^*2+1$	-127734702	$(9-8^*7^*6)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-120707937	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))^*2-1$	-127996621	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-120707955	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))^*2+1$	-127996655	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
-120708009	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))^*2-1$	-127996689	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
-120943100	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(32+1)-1)$	-127996723	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
-120943244	$-9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(32+1)-1)$	-128007501	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-121178398	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(32+1)+1)$	-128007535	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
-121178542	$-9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(32+1)+1))$	-128007569	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$
-121372200	$9-(8+7^*65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-128007603	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
-121373126	$9-(8+7^*65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-128024034	$9-(8^*7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21$
-121617853	$-9/(87-6/(5+4))^{\wedge}3-3^*21$	-128024094	$-9-(8^*7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21$
-121634343	$9+8*(7-65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-128367872	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3^*2-1$
-121634729	$(9-8^{\wedge}7^*6)^*(5^*4/3+2+1)$	-128372526	$9^{\wedge}8*((7+6)^*(5+4)^{\wedge}3-2-1)$
-121634815	$9+8*((7-65)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-128445954	$98*(7^*6-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-121634817	$-9+8*((7-65)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-128446346	$98*(7^*6-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-121635271	$9+8*(7-65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-128446542	$98*(7^*6-5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-121896486	$9-(87+6)^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-128446934	$98*(7^*6-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-121896858	$9-(87+6)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-128450168	$-98*(7-6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-121897044	$9-(87+6)^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-128450756	$-98*(7-6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-121897416	$9-(87+6)^*5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-128451148	$-98*(7-6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-122001996	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3-2)+1)$	-128451344	$-98*(7+6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-122002030	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$	-128451736	$-98*(7+6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-123046804	$9*(8-7*(6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-128451932	$-98*(7+6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-123046946	$-9*(8+7*(6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-128452324	$-98*(7+6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-123046948	$-9*(8+7*(6-5+4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-128454578	$-98*(7^*6+5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-123996759	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$	-128455166	$-98*(7^*6+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-123996793	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2)+1)$	-128603170	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3^*2+1$
-124002029	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^*3+2)-1)$	-128615328	$-9/(8+7)*((6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-124002063	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^*3+2)+1)$	-128993283	$(9^{\wedge}8-765^*4^{\wedge}3)^*(-2-1)$
-124007299	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$	-129022065	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)^*2-1)$
-124007333	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2)+1)$	-129091143	$(9^{\wedge}8-76^*5^*4^*3)^*(-2-1)$
-124232055	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4*(32+1)$	-129103227	$(9^{\wedge}8-76^*5^*4^*3)^*(-2-1)$
-124232073	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4*(32+1)$	-129112623	$(9^{\wedge}8-765^*4^*3)^*(-2-1)$
-124236675	$9-(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4*(32+1)$	-129118986	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7+6)^*543)^*(-2-1)$
-124237995	$9-(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4*(32+1)$	-129124098	$(9^{\wedge}8-765*(4+3))^*(-2-1)$
-124242615	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4*(32+1)$	-129128535	$(9^{\wedge}8-76*(54-3))^*(-2-1)$
-124354984	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)^*(-4+3^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	-129129219	$(9^{\wedge}8-76*(5+43))^*(-2-1)$
-124359404	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)^*(-4+3^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	-129129714	$(9^{\wedge}8-(76+5)^*43)^*(-2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-129130875	$(9^8 - (7+65)*43)*(-2-1)$	-132153327	$-9*(8*7*(65+4^3*2)-1)$
-129131499	$(9^8+76*(5-43))*(-2-1)$	-132153345	$-9*(8*7*(65+4^3*2)+1)$
-129132603	$(9^8-7*6*5*4*3)*(-2-1)$	-132153408	$-9*8*(7*(65+4^3*2)+1)$
-129132681	$(9^8+(7-65)*43)*(-2-1)$	-132590325	$-98*(7^6*(5*4+3)/2-1)$
-129133242	$(9^8-(765+4)*3)*(-2-1)$	-132590521	$-98*(7^6*(5*4+3)/2+1)$
-129133314	$(9^8-(765-4)*3)*(-2-1)$	-133649255	$9+8*7^6*(5-(4+3)*21)$
-129134214	$(9^8-(7+654)*3)*(-2-1)$	-133920752	$(-9^8+765)*(4+3^{\wedge}2-2-1)$
-129134340	$(9^8+(7-654)*3)*(-2-1)$	-133925512	$(9^8+765)*(-4-3^{\wedge}2+2+1)$
-129135753	$(-9^8+7*6*5*(4+3))*(2+1)$	-133955073	$(9-8*(7+6)*5)*(4^3*2-1)$
-129136059	$(9^8-76*54/3)*(-2-1)$	-133956095	$(9-8*(7+6)*5)*(4^3*2+1)$
-129136761	$(-9^8+7*6*(5+4)*3)*(2+1)$	-134002194	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5+4^3*2)-1)$
-129137103	$(9^8-765*4/3)*(-2-1)$	-134002228	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5+4^3*2)+1)$
-129137265	$(9^8-7*6*(5*4+3))*(-2-1)$	-134472735	$9*(8+7^6*(5-4*(3+1)))$
-129137391	$(-9^8+7*(6+5)*4*3)*(2+1)$	-134472879	$9*(-8+7^6*(5-4*(3+1)))$
-129137580	$(9^8-7*(6*5*4+3))*(-2-1)$	-134479287	$9*(8^7-65*(4^3*2-1))$
-129137706	$(9^8-7*(6*5*4-3))*(-2-1)$	-134480457	$9*(8^7-65*(4^3*2+1))$
-129137823	$(-9^8+(7+6)*5*4*3)*(2+1)$	-134741824	$-9*(87/(6^5-4))^{\wedge}3*21$
-129138021	$(9^8-7*6*(5+4)*3)*(-2-1)$	-134765280	$(-9-8*7*6)*5*(5^4*(3/2)-1)$
-129138237	$(-9^8+(7*6*5+4)*3)*(2+1)$	-134765970	$(-9-8*7*6)*(5^4*(3/2)+1)$
-129138471	$(9^8-(7*6+5)*4*3)*(-2-1)$	-135523575	$9*((8-(7^6-5)*4)*3+2+1)$
-129139323	$(9^8-7*6*5*4/3)*(-2-1)$	-135523593	$9*((8-(7^6-5)*4)*3-2-1)$
-129139335	$(9^8+(7-6*5)*4*3)*(-2-1)$	-135527922	$9-(87*6-5)*(4^3*2-1)$
-129139502	$(9^8-(7+654)/3)*(-2-1)$	-135528495	$(9-8*7)*((6+5)*4^3*2+1)$
-129139516	$(9^8+(7-654)/3)*(-2-1)$	-135528956	$9-(87*6-5)*(4^3*2+1)$
-129140810	$(9^8-(7-654)/3)*(-2-1)$	-136314313	$-9+8*(7-65*(4^3*2-1))$
-129140824	$(9^8+(7+654)/3)*(-2-1)$	-136314407	$-9-8*(7+65*(4^3*2-1))$
-129140991	$(9^8-(7-6*5)*4*3)*(-2-1)$	-136315335	$9+8*(7-65*(4^3*2+1))$
-129141003	$(9^8+7*6*5*4/3)*(-2-1)$	-136315353	$-9+8*(7-65*(4^3*2+1))$
-129141855	$(9^8+(7*6+5)*4*3)*(-2-1)$	-136315447	$9-8*(7+65*(4^3*2+1))$
-129142089	$(9^8+(7*6*5+4)*3)*(-2-1)$	-136590561	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+4*(3-1)))$
-129142305	$(9^8+7*(6*5+4)*3)*(-2-1)$	-136836027	$9+87*6*(5-4^3*2+1)$
-129142503	$(9^8+(7+6)*5*4*3)*(-2-1)$	-136836462	$9+87*(6*(5-4^3*2)+1)$
-129142620	$(9^8+7*(6*5*4-3))*(-2-1)$	-136836480	$-9+87*(6*(5-4^3*2)+1)$
-129142746	$(9^8+7*(6*5*4+3))*(-2-1)$	-136836636	$9+87*(6*(5-4^3*2)-1)$
-129142935	$(9^8+7*(6+5)*4*3)*(-2-1)$	-136836654	$-9+87*(6*(5-4^3*2)-1)$
-129143061	$(9^8+7*6*(5*4+3))*(-2-1)$	-136837071	$9+87*6*(5-4^3*2-1)$
-129143223	$(9^8+765*4/3)*(-2-1)$	-136838574	$9*(8+(7-65)*(4^3*2-1))$
-129143565	$(9^8+7*6*(5+4)*3)*(-2-1)$	-136838718	$9*(-8+(7-65)*(4^3*2-1))$
-129144267	$(9^8+76*54/3)*(-2-1)$	-136839618	$9*(8+(7-65)*(4^3*2+1))$
-129144573	$(9^8+7*6*5*(4+3))*(-2-1)$	-136839762	$9*(-8+(7-65)*(4^3*2+1))$
-129145986	$(9^8-(7-654)*3)*(-2-1)$	-136841247	$9-87*6*(5+4^3*2-1)$
-129146112	$(9^8+(7+654)*3)*(-2-1)$	-136841682	$9-87*(6*(5+4^3*2)-1)$
-129147012	$(9^8+(765-4)*3)*(-2-1)$	-136841856	$9-87*(6*(5+4^3*2)+1)$
-129147084	$(9^8+(765+4)*3)*(-2-1)$	-136842291	$9-87*6*(5+4^3*2+1)$
-129147645	$(9^8-(7-65)*43)*(-2-1)$	-138002226	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5+4^3)-2-1)$
-129147723	$(9^8+7*6*5*4*3)*(-2-1)$	-138002260	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5+4^3)-2+1)$
-129148827	$(9^8-76*(5-43))*(-2-1)$	-138002294	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5+4^3)+2-1)$
-129149451	$(9^8+(7+65)*43)*(-2-1)$	-138002328	$(-9-8)*(7^6*(5+4^3)+2+1)$
-129150612	$(9^8+(76+5)*43)*(-2-1)$	-138149352	$9-(87*6+5)*(4^3*2-1)$
-129151107	$(9^8+76*(5+43))*(-2-1)$	-138150406	$9-(87*6+5)*(4^3*2+1)$
-129151791	$(9^8+76*(54-3))*(-2-1)$	-138150424	$-9-(87*6+5)*(4^3*2+1)$
-129156228	$(9^8+765*(4+3))*(-2-1)$	-138347286	$-98*((7^6-5)*4*3-21)$
-129161340	$(9^8+(7+6)*543)*(-2-1)$	-138349295	$-98*((7^6-5)*4*3-2^{\wedge}2-1)$
-129167703	$(9^8+765*4*3)*(-2-1)$	-138351402	$-98*((7^6-5)*4*3+21)$
-129177099	$(9^8+76*54*3)*(-2-1)$	-138354480	$9-(8*7^6*5)*(4+3)*21$
-129189183	$(9^8+76*5*43)*(-2-1)$	-138354930	$-98*(7^6*(5+4+3)-2-1)$
-129258261	$9^8*((7-6+(5+4))^{\wedge}3)*(-2-1)$	-138355175	$98*(7^6*(5-4-3)+2^{\wedge}2-1)$
-129287043	$(9^8+765*4^3)*(-2-1)$	-138355273	$98*(7^6*(5-4-3)-2^{\wedge}2-1)$
-129311424	$9*(8/7-6^{\wedge}5)*(4^3*2-1)$	-138355518	$-98*(7^6*(5+4+3)+2+1)$
-129349440	$9*(8/7+6^{\wedge}5)*(-4^3*2+1)$	-138355950	$9-(8*7^6*5)*(4+3)*21$
-129907800	$9^8*((-7-6)/(5+4))^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	-138359046	$-98*((7^6+5)*4*3-21)$
-130002128	$(-9-8)*(7^6*5*(4+3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-138363162	$-98*((7^6+5)*4*3+21)$
-130002162	$(-9-8)*(7^6*5*(4+3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-138673647	$(-9-8*(7+6)*5)*(4^3*2-1)$
-131290776	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*4*(3-1))$	-139531714	$(98/7)^{\wedge}6*(5^4/-3-2+1)$
-131301936	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*4*(3-1))$	-139761000	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*4*(3+1))$
-131620221	$9^8*(7*6/(-5-4))^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	-139761144	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*4*(3+1))$
-131766863	$9+8*(7^6*5*(4-3)+1)$	-139767003	$9*(8*7^6*(5-43/2)+1)$
-131996551	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)*(4^3+2)-1)$	-139773024	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*4*(3+1))$
-131996585	$(-9-8)*((7^6-5)*(4^3+2)+1)$	-139979672	$-98*(7^6+5*(4^3*2-1))$
-132007771	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5)*(4^3+2)-1)$	-139980064	$-98*(7^6+5*4^3*2-1)$
-132007805	$(-9-8)*((7^6+5)*(4^3+2)+1)$	-139980260	$-98*(7^6+5*4^3*2+1)$
-132153264	$-9*8*(7*(65+4^3*2)-1)$	-139980652	$-98*(7^6+5*(4^3*2+1))$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-140002293	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*(4*3+2)-1)$	-149422194	$(9*8+7*6)*(-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-140002327	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5*(4*3+2)+1)$	-149878358	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4+3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-140824341	$(9*8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*21$	-149878554	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4+3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-140825496	$(9+8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*21$	-149884728	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1)$
-140825676	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*21$	-149884924	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3/2))+1)$
-140825694	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*21$	-149891098	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-140825832	$(9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*21$	-149891294	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-140825836	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)*21$	-150355350	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4+3)*21))$
-140825852	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)*21$	-150355494	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4+3)*21))$
-140825854	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)*21$	-150589679	$9-8*((7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*32-1)$
-140825870	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)*21$	-150589695	$9-8*((7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*32+1)$
-140825874	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*-21$	-150591727	$9-8*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*32-1)$
-140826012	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*21$	-150591743	$9-8*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*32+1)$
-140826030	$-9*(8/(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)))*21$	-150591745	$-9-8*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*32-1)$
-140826210	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*-21$	-151052319	$9+(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4)*321$
-140827365	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*(54+3))*-21$	-151052337	$-9+(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4)*321$
-142002326	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$	-151070295	$9-(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4)*321$
-142002360	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	-151070313	$-9-(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4)*321$
-142805189	$(-9-8/(7/65^{\wedge}4*3))*21$	-151414704	$-98*((7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-142943607	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(3/2+1))$	-151414900	$-98*((7-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-143370972	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7/6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)*2-1)$	-152002499	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(54*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-143426944	$9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-321)$	-152403120	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3-21)$
-144002231	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-3)-2)+1$	-152464356	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-54)*(3-21)$
-144002233	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-3)-2)-1$	-152466551	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)/(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-144002357	$-9*(8/(7^{\wedge}6-6/(5*4-3))-2)+1$	-152466553	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)/(4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-144002395	$-9*(8/(7^{\wedge}6-6/(5*4-3))+2)-1$	-152466695	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-144002519	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-3)+2)+1$	-152466697	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-144002521	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-3)+2)-1$	-152471376	$(9*8-7^{\wedge}6*54)*(3+21)$
-145198830	$9^{\wedge}8-(7+6)^{\wedge}(-5+4*3)*(2+1)$	-152471592	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*54/3-21)$
-145765053	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))*21$	-152472696	$(9+8-7^{\wedge}6*54)*(3+21)$
-145766934	$9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))*21$	-152472903	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*54)*(3+21)$
-145766952	$-9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))*21$	-152472915	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*54/3-21)$
-145767013	$98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	-152472921	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*54)*(3+21)$
-145767209	$-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)*21$	-152472951	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54/3-2)-1)$
-145767270	$9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))*21$	-152472969	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54/3-2)+1)$
-145767288	$-9-(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))*21$	-152473071	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*54*3-2-1)$
-145769169	$(-98+7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3))*21$	-152473089	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*54*3-2-1)$
-145883759	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*(32-1)$	-152473091	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*54*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-145884481	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	-152473119	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*54*3+2+1)$
-145884627	$9-(8*7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*(32-1)$	-152473239	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54/3+2)-1)$
-145885039	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	-152473257	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*54/3+2)+1)$
-145885743	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*(32-1)$	-152473287	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(3+21)$
-146237609	$98-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$	-152473293	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*54/3+21)$
-146237635	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$	-152473305	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(3+21)$
-146237779	$9*-8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$	-152473512	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(-3-21)$
-146237805	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2-1)$	-152474616	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*54/3+21)$
-146472907	$98-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$	-152474832	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(-3-21)$
-146472933	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$	-152479511	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)/(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-146473077	$9*-8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$	-152479513	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)/(4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-146473103	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4-3)*2+1)$	-152479655	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1$
-147649397	$98-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$	-152479657	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1$
-147649423	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$	-152481852	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+54)*(3-21)$
-147649567	$9*-8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$	-152543088	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(3-21)$
-147649593	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2-1)$	-152943691	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(54*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-147884695	$98-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$	-153352872	$9*(87-65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-147884721	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$	-153353151	$9*(8*7-65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-147884865	$9*-8-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$	-153353448	$9*(87-65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-147884891	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*((5^{\wedge}4+3)*2+1)$	-153353456	$9*(87-65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-148132904	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321)$	-153353458	$9*(87-65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-148237821	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-32)-1)$	-153353466	$9*(87-65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-148239747	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-32)+1)$	-153353664	$-9*(8-7+65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-148603500	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*54*(2+1)$	-153353745	$9*(8*7-65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-148897215	$9-8*(76-5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-153353790	$-9*(8+7+65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-148897775	$9-8*((76-5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-153354042	$9*(87-65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-148897791	$9-8*((76-5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-153354169	$9*(8-(7+6)*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-148897793	$-9-8*((76-5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-153354258	$-9*(8-7+65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-148898351	$9-8*(76-5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-153354311	$-9*(8+(7+6)*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-148898369	$-9-8*(76-5)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-153354313	$-9*(8+(7+6)*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-149296509	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54*3-21))$	-153354366	$-9*(8+7+65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-149296653	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54*3-21))$	-153354384	$-9*(8+7+65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-149334921	$9^{\wedge}8*(-76/54/3-2-1)$	-153354438	$-9*(87+65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-149421966	$(9*8+7*6)*(-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-153354735	$-9*(8*7+65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-153354834	$-9*(8-7+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1))$	-159381111	$9+8*76*(5-4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-153354960	$-9*(8+7+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1))$	-159385975	$9-8*76*(5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-153355014	$-9*(87+65*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-159386575	$9-8*(76*(5+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$
-153355022	$-9*(87+65*4^3\wedge 2)+1$	-159386591	$9-8*(76*(5+4^3\wedge 2)+1)$
-153355024	$-9*(87+65*4^3\wedge 2)-1$	-159387191	$9-8*76*(5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-153355032	$-9*(87+65*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-159432300	$9\wedge 8*(-7+(6/(5+4)))^3+2+1$
-153355329	$-9*(8*7+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1))$	-159662506	$9\wedge 8+7\wedge 6*(5-(4^3)^{(2+1)})$
-153355608	$-9*(87+65*(4^3\wedge 2+1))$	-160133102	$9\wedge 8-7\wedge 6*(54^*32-1)$
-153897705	$9\wedge 8-7\wedge 6*54^*(32-1)$	-160242111	$9\wedge 8-(7\wedge 6-5)^*(4^3)^{(2+1)}$
-154137830	$-98*(7-6*(5-4^3\wedge 2+1))$	-160259391	$9\wedge 8-(7\wedge 6+5)^*(4^3)^{(2+1)}$
-154138320	$-98*(7-6*(5-4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	-160368400	$9\wedge 8-7\wedge 6*(54^*32+1)$
-154138516	$-98*(7-6*(5-4^3\wedge 2)+1)$	-160408458	$-98*(7\wedge 6*5+4\wedge(3^2+1))$
-154139006	$-98*(7-6*(5-4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	-160435179	$9*(8-76)^*(5+4^3\wedge 2)+1$
-154142338	$98*(7-6*(5+4^3\wedge 2-1))$	-160435197	$9*(8-76)^*(5+4^3\wedge 2)-1$
-154143514	$98*(7-6*(5+4^3\wedge 2+1))$	-160693650	$9-(8*76+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-154143710	$-98*(7+6*(5+4^3\wedge 2-1))$	-160694876	$9-(8*76+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-154144200	$-98*(7+6*(5+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	-160694894	$-9-(8*76+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-154144396	$-98*(7+6*(5+4^3\wedge 2)+1)$	-160838996	$9\wedge 8-7\wedge 6*(5+(4^3)^{(2+1)))$
-154144886	$-98*(7+6*(5+4^3\wedge 2+1))$	-162002601	$9*(8-7\wedge 6*(54-3)^*(2+1))$
-154355471	$9-8*(7\wedge 6*(54^*3+2)-1)$	-162002656	$(-9-8)^*(7\wedge 6*(5+4)^*3\wedge 2-1)$
-154355487	$9-8*(7\wedge 6*(54^*3+2)+1)$	-162002745	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*(54-3)^*(2+1))$
-154590786	$(98/7)\wedge 6*(5^4/32-1)$	-162620925	$9\wedge 8*(-7*6/54-3)+21$
-154844704	$-98*((7+6*5^4/3)^2-1)$	-162620967	$9\wedge 8*(-7*6/54-3)-21$
-154844900	$-98*((7+6*5^4/3)^2+1)$	-162901240	$9-(8/76/5)^{\wedge-4}*32+1$
-155295615	$9-8*(7\wedge 6*5-4)^*(32+1)$	-162901242	$9-(8/76/5)^{\wedge-4}*32-1$
-155296539	$9-(8*7\wedge 6*5-4)^*(32+1)$	-164119311	$-9*(8+(7\wedge 6*5-4)^*(32-1))$
-155296803	$9-(8*7\wedge 6*5+4)^*(32+1)$	-164121543	$-9*(8+(7\wedge 6*5+4)^*(32-1))$
-155297727	$9-8*(7\wedge 6*5+4)^*(32+1)$	-164178520	$(9-8*7)^*((6-5\wedge 4*3)^2-1)$
-155297745	$-9-8*(7\wedge 6*5+4)^*(32+1)$	-164178614	$(9-8*7)^*((6-5\wedge 4*3)^2+1)$
-155642940	$9*(8-(7\wedge 6-5)^*(4+3)^*21)$	-164602270	$-98*((7-6+5)\wedge 4\wedge(3/2)-1)$
-155643084	$-9*(8+(7\wedge 6-5)^*(4+3)^*21)$	-164602466	$-98*((7-6+5)\wedge 4\wedge(3/2)+1)$
-1556449529	$-98*(7\wedge 6*(5+4)^*3/2-1)$	-164888559	$(-9-8)^*((7+6*5)^*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-155649725	$-98*(7\wedge 6*(5+4)^*3/2+1)$	-165009498	$(9\wedge 8-765)^*(-4+(3^2)^{\wedge-1})$
-155656314	$-9*(8+(7\wedge 6+5)^*(4+3)^*21)$	-165015363	$(9\wedge 8+765)^*(-4+(3^2)^{\wedge-1})$
-155823750	$9\wedge 8*76/(5^{\wedge-4}*3-21)$	-165041955	$(9\wedge 8+76*54^3)^*(-2-1)$
-155974949	$(9+8)^*(7*(6-5*4^3\wedge 2)+1)$	-166293520	$(9-8*7)^*((6+5\wedge 4*3)^2-1)$
-155974983	$(9+8)^*(7*(6-5*4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	-166293614	$(9-8*7)^*((6+5\wedge 4*3)^2+1)$
-155976377	$(-9-8)^*(7*(6+5*4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	-166590957	$(9+8*7\wedge 6*(5-4\wedge 3))^*(2+1)$
-155976411	$(-9-8)^*(7*(6+5*4^3\wedge 2)+1)$	-166591011	$(-9+8*7\wedge 6*(5-4\wedge 3))^*(2+1)$
-156049983	$9*(8/7+65)^*(-4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-166603797	$9\wedge 8-7\wedge 6*54^*(32+1)$
-157492674	$9\wedge 8-765*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-167509449	$-9*(8+(76-5)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1))$
-157494204	$9\wedge 8-765*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-167509935	$9*(8-(76-5)^*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-157531913	$98+7\wedge 6*(5-4^3*21)$	-167510079	$-9*(8+(76-5)^*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-157532109	$-98+7\wedge 6*(5-4^3*21)$	-167510097	$-9*(8+(76-5)^*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-157837929	$((9\wedge 8-7)^*(-6-5)+4)/3+21$	-167510583	$9*(8-(76-5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1))$
-157838025	$((9\wedge 8+7)^*(-6-5)-4)/3-21$	-167510727	$-9*(8+(76-5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1))$
-158072220	$9-(8*76-5)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-169411095	$9*(8-7\wedge 6*5+4)^*32+1$
-158073426	$9-(8*76-5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-169411113	$9*(8-7\wedge 6*5+4)^*32-1$
-158111478	$(98-(7\wedge 6-5)^*4\wedge 3)^*21$	-169411671	$-9*(8/7^{\wedge-6}*5^4-321)$
-158113359	$9+(8-(7\wedge 6-5)^*4\wedge 3)^*21$	-169413399	$9*(8-(7\wedge 6*5-4)^*32+1)$
-158113377	$-9+(8-(7\wedge 6-5)^*4\wedge 3)^*21$	-169413417	$9*(8-(7\wedge 6*5-4)^*32-1)$
-158113438	$98-(7\wedge 6-5)^*4\wedge 3^*21$	-169413471	$-9*(8+(7\wedge 6*5-4)^*32-1)$
-158113634	$-98-(7\wedge 6-5)^*4\wedge 3^*21$	-169413489	$-9*(8+(7\wedge 6*5-4)^*32+1)$
-158113695	$9-(8+(7\wedge 6-5)^*4\wedge 3)^*21$	-169414325	$9*(-8*(7\wedge 6*5^4-3)+2)+1$
-158113713	$-9-(8+(7\wedge 6-5)^*4\wedge 3)^*21$	-169414327	$9*(-8*(7\wedge 6*5^4-3)+2)-1$
-158115594	$(98+(7\wedge 6-5)^*4\wedge 3)^*-21$	-169414361	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5^4-3)+2)+1$
-158124918	$(98-(7\wedge 6+5)^*4\wedge 3)^*21$	-169414363	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5^4-3)+2)-1$
-158126799	$9+(8-(7\wedge 6+5)^*4\wedge 3)^*21$	-169414451	$-9*8*(7\wedge 6*5^4-3/2)+1$
-158126817	$-9+(8-(7\wedge 6+5)^*4\wedge 3)^*21$	-169414453	$-9*8*(7\wedge 6*5^4-3/2)-1$
-158126878	$98-(7\wedge 6+5)^*4\wedge 3^*21$	-169414667	$9*8*(7\wedge 6*5^4-3/2)+1$
-158127074	$-98-(7\wedge 6+5)^*4\wedge 3^*21$	-169414669	$9*8*(7\wedge 6*5^4-3/2)-1$
-158127135	$9-(8+(7\wedge 6+5)^*4\wedge 3)^*21$	-169414757	$9*(-8*(7\wedge 6*5^4+3)+2)+1$
-158127153	$-9-(8+(7\wedge 6+5)^*4\wedge 3)^*21$	-169414759	$9*(-8*(7\wedge 6*5^4+3)+2)-1$
-158129034	$(98+(7\wedge 6+5)^*4\wedge 3)^*-21$	-169414793	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5^4+3)+2)+1$
-158708403	$98-7\wedge 6*(5+4^3*21)$	-169414795	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6*5^4+3)+2)-1$
-158708599	$-98-7\wedge 6*(5+4^3*21)$	-169415631	$9*(8-(7\wedge 6*5+4)^*32+1)$
-158721314	$9\wedge 8-7\wedge 6*5*(4+3)^{(2+1)}$	-169415775	$-9*(8+(7\wedge 6*5+4)^*32-1)$
-159379895	$9+8*76*(5-4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-169415793	$-9*(8+(7\wedge 6*5+4)^*32+1)$
-159380495	$9+8*(76*(5-4^3\wedge 2)+1)$	-169417449	$-9*(8/7^{\wedge-6}*5^4+321)$
-159380511	$9+8*(76*(5-4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	-169418007	$-9*((8+7\wedge 6*5+4)^*32-1)$
-159380513	$-9+8*(76*(5-4^3\wedge 2)+1)$	-169868655	$9-8*(76+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-159380529	$-9+8*(76*(5-4^3\wedge 2)-1)$	-169869951	$9-8*(76+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-169921779	$9-87*((6-5+4)^3\wedge 2-1)$	-177427505	$9\wedge 8-7\wedge 6*(5\wedge 4*3-2+1)$
-169921953	$9-87*((6-5+4)^3\wedge 2+1)$	-177662803	$9\wedge 8-7\wedge 6*(5\wedge 4*3+2-1)$
-170355749	$(9-8*7\wedge 6*543)/(2+1)$	-177799104	$-9*8*(7\wedge 6-54-3)*21$
-170355755	$(-9-8*7\wedge 6*543)/(2+1)$	-177803073	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6-54-3)*21)$
-170471343	$(98-7\wedge 6*(5+4\wedge 3))^*21$	-177804207	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6-54)+3)*21$
-170473224	$9+(8-7\wedge 6*(5+4\wedge 3))^*21$	-177808176	$-9*8*(7\wedge 6-54+3)*21$
-170473242	$-9+(8-7\wedge 6*(5+4\wedge 3))^*21$	-177812712	$-9*8*(7\wedge 6-5-43)*21$
-170473303	$98-7\wedge 6*(5+4\wedge 3)*21$	-177827832	$-9*8*(7\wedge 6+5-43)*21$
-170473499	$-98-7\wedge 6*(5+4\wedge 3)*21$	-177844653	$-9*(8/7\wedge 6-5*43)*21$
-170473560	$9-(8+7\wedge 6*(5+4\wedge 3))^*21$	-177854670	$-9*(8/7\wedge 6-54*3)*21$
-170473578	$-9-(8+7\wedge 6*(5+4\wedge 3))^*21$	-177858072	$-9*8*(7\wedge 6-54/3)*21$
-170475459	$(98+7\wedge 6*(5+4\wedge 3))^*-21$	-177869601	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6-5)-43)*21$
-170826348	$9*8*7\wedge 6*(-5*4-(3*2)\wedge -1)$	-177878106	$-9*(8*7\wedge 6+5-43)*21$
-171164816	$9*8-(7*(6-5\wedge 4*3))^{\wedge 2+1}$	-177884775	$9-8*(7\wedge 6*(5+4)-3)*21$
-171164818	$9*8-(7*(6-5\wedge 4*3))^{\wedge 2-1}$	-177885342	$9-(8*7\wedge 6*(5+4)+3)*21$
-171414495	$98-7\wedge 6*((5+4)\wedge 3*2-1)$	-177885783	$9-8*(7\wedge 6*(5+4)+3)*21$
-171414521	$9*8-7\wedge 6*((5+4)\wedge 3*2-1)$	-177885801	$-9-8*(7\wedge 6*(5+4)+3)*21$
-171414665	$9*(8-7\wedge 6*(5+4)\wedge 3*2-1)$	-177894927	$-9*(8*7\wedge 6+54*3)*21$
-171414691	$-98-7\wedge 6*((5+4)\wedge 3*2-1)$	-177896061	$-9*(8*7\wedge 6+54+3)*21$
-171531837	$9*((8-7\wedge 6*54)*3+21)$	-177898101	$9\wedge 8-7\wedge 6*(5\wedge 4*3+2+1)$
-171531981	$9*(8-7\wedge 6*54*3+21)$	-177900975	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6+5)+43)*21$
-171531999	$9*((8-7\wedge 6*54)*3+2+1)$	-177912504	$-9*8*(7\wedge 6+54/3)*21$
-171532053	$9*((8-7\wedge 6*54)*3-2-1)$	-177942744	$-9*8*(7\wedge 6-5+43)*21$
-171532125	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*54*3-21)$	-177957864	$-9*8*(7\wedge 6+5+43)*21$
-171532149	$9*(8-7\wedge 6*54*3)+21$	-177962400	$-9*8*(7\wedge 6+54-3)*21$
-171532191	$9*(8-7\wedge 6*54*3)-21$	-177966369	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6+54)-3)*21$
-171532287	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*54*3-2-1)$	-177967503	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6+54)+3)*21$
-171532293	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*54*3)+21$	-177971472	$-9*8*(7\wedge 6+54+3)*21$
-171532305	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*54*3-2+1)$	-178603995	$9\wedge 8-7\wedge 6*(5\wedge 4+3)*(2+1)$
-171532323	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*54*3+2-1)$	-179302464	$-9*(8-76*(5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1))$
-171532335	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*54*3)-21$	-179303139	$-9*(8-76*(5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$
-171532359	$9*(8-7\wedge 6*54*3-21)$	-179303157	$-9*(8-76*(5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$
-171532395	$-9*(8+(7\wedge 6*54+3)*(2+1))$	-179303832	$-9*(8-76*(5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1))$
-171532431	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*54)*3-2-1)$	-179309160	$9*(8-76*(5+4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1))$
-171532503	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*54*3+21)$	-179309304	$-9*(8+76*(5+4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1))$
-171532647	$-9*((8+7\wedge 6*54)*3+21)$	-179309979	$-9*(8+76*(5+4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$
-171649793	$98-7\wedge 6*((5+4)\wedge 3*2+1)$	-179309997	$-9*(8+76*(5+4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$
-171649819	$98-7\wedge 6*((5+4)\wedge 3*2+1)$	-179310528	$9*(8-76*(5+4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1))$
-171649963	$9*-8-7\wedge 6*((5+4)\wedge 3*2+1)$	-179310672	$-9*(8+76*(5+4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1))$
-171649989	$-98-7\wedge 6*((5+4)\wedge 3*2+1)$	-179358150	$(9\wedge 8-765)*(-4-(3*2)\wedge -1)$
-172002821	$(-9-8)*(7\wedge 6*(54+32)-1)$	-179364525	$(9\wedge 8+765)*(-4-(3*2)\wedge -1)$
-172002855	$(-9-8)*(7\wedge 6*(54+32)+1)$	-179785508	$98*7*(65-4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1)$
-172168572	$(9\wedge 8-7*654)*(-3-2+1)$	-179786096	$98*(7*(65-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$
-172170468	$(9\wedge 8-76*54)*(-3-2+1)$	-179786193	$98*7*(65-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1$
-172174644	$(9\wedge 8-765*4)*(-3-2+1)$	-179786195	$98*7*(65-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1$
-172185600	$9\wedge 8*(7-6-5)+4*321$	-179786292	$98*(7*(65-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$
-172186119	$(9\wedge 8-765/4)*(-3-2+1)$	-179786880	$98*7*(65-4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1)$
-172187649	$(9\wedge 8+765/4)*(-3-2+1)$	-179810106	$98*(7*(6*5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$
-172188168	$9\wedge 8*(7-6-5)-4*321$	-179823140	$98*(7*(6+5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$
-172199124	$(9\wedge 8+765*4)*(-3-2+1)$	-179823336	$98*(7*(6+5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$
-172203300	$(9\wedge 8+76*54)*(-3-2+1)$	-179830000	$98*(7*(6-5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$
-172205196	$(9\wedge 8+7*654)*(-3-2+1)$	-179830196	$98*(7*(6-5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$
-172228023	$-9*(8\wedge 7+65*(4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1))$	-179830686	$-98*(7*(6-5)*4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1)$
-172229193	$-9*(8\wedge 7+65*(4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1))$	-179830882	$-98*(7*(6-5)*4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1)$
-172541178	$9\wedge 8*(-7-6\wedge -5*4\wedge 3+2+1)$	-179851266	$-98*(7*(6*5+4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$
-172591011	$9*(8-7\wedge 6*(54*3+2-1))$	-179851462	$-98*(7*(6*5+4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$
-172591155	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*(54*3+2-1))$	-179874688	$-98*7*(65+4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1)$
-172931388	$-98*(7\wedge 6*5-43)*(2+1)$	-179875276	$-98*(7*(65+4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$
-172945157	$-98*((7\wedge 6*5+4)*3-2\wedge -1)$	-179875373	$98*7*(-65-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1$
-172956672	$-98*(7\wedge 6*5+43)*(2+1)$	-179875375	$98*7*(-65-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1$
-173369816	$9*8-(7*(6+5\wedge 4*3))^{\wedge 2+1}$	-179875472	$-98*(7*(65+4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$
-173369818	$9*8-(7*(6+5\wedge 4*3))^{\wedge 2-1}$	-179876060	$-98*7*(65+4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1)$
-173649987	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*(54*3+2)-1)$	-180701157	$(9-8*(7\wedge 6-5)*4\wedge 3)*(2+1)$
-173650005	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*(54*3+2)+1)$	-180701211	$(-9-8*(7\wedge 6-5)*4\wedge 3)*(2+1)$
-174496350	$98*(7*(6\wedge 5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$	-180707877	$(9-(8*7\wedge 6-5)*4\wedge 3)*(2+1)$
-174496546	$98*(7*(6\wedge 5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$	-180707931	$(9+(8*7\wedge 6-5)*4\wedge -3)*(2+1)$
-174707649	$-9*(8+(7\wedge 6*5-4)*(32+1))$	-180709797	$(9-(8*7\wedge 6+5)/4\wedge -3)*(2+1)$
-174709881	$9*(8-(7\wedge 6*5+4)*(32+1))$	-180709851	$(9+(8*7\wedge 6+5)/4\wedge -3)*(2-1)$
-174710025	$-9*(8+(7\wedge 6*5+4)*(32+1))$	-180716517	$(9-8*(7\wedge 6+5)*4\wedge 3)*(2+1)$
-176160512	$(9-8*7)*((6+5)*4)\wedge (3+2-1)$	-180716571	$(-9-8*(7\wedge 6+5)*4\wedge 3)*(2+1)$
-176486313	$9\wedge 8-7\wedge 6*(5\wedge 4-3)*(2+1)$	-181061739	$9*(8-7\wedge 6*(54+3))*(2+1)$
-177192207	$9\wedge 8-7\wedge 6*(5\wedge 4*3-2-1)$	-181061883	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*(54+3))*(2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-181665099	$(9*8-765)*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-191179950	$(9-8+7\wedge 6*5)*(-4-321)$
-181665721	$9*(8-7*(6+5)*4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1$	-191182216	$9-(8+7\wedge 6*5)*(4+321)$
-181665863	$-9*(8+7*(6+5)*4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1$	-191182234	$-9-(8+7\wedge 6*5)*(4+321)$
-181665865	$-9*(8+7*(6+5)*4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1$	-191185150	$(9+8+7\wedge 6*5)*(-4-321)$
-181666485	$(9*8-765)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-191203025	$(9*8+7\wedge 6*5)*(-4-321)$
-182112840	$-9*8*((7\wedge 6-5)*43/2-1)$	-191406838	$-98*(7+(6-5+4)\wedge 3\wedge 2-1)$
-182112903	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6-5)*43/2-1)$	-191407034	$-98*(7+(6-5+4)\wedge 3\wedge 2+1)$
-182112921	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6-5)*43/2+1)$	-191650005	$(9*8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 3)*(2+1)$
-182112984	$-9*8*((7\wedge 6-5)*43/2+1)$	-191650170	$(9+8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 3)*(2+1)$
-182128320	$-9*8*((7\wedge 6+5)*43/2-1)$	-191650188	$9+(8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 3)*(2+1)$
-182128383	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6+5)*43/2-1)$	-191650197	$9*(8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 3)/(2+1)$
-182128401	$-9*(8*(7\wedge 6+5)*43/2+1)$	-191650206	$-9+(8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 3)*(2+1)$
-182128464	$-9*8*((7\wedge 6+5)*43/2+1)$	-191650218	$(9-8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 3)*(2+1)$
-182452205	$-9*(8\wedge 7*(6+5-4/3)-2)+1$	-191650224	$(9-8+7\wedge 6*5\wedge 3)*(-2-1)$
-182452207	$-9*(8\wedge 7*(6+5-4/3)-2)-1$	-191650236	$9-(8+7\wedge 6*5\wedge 3)*(2+1)$
-182452241	$9*(-8\wedge 7*(6+5-4/3)-2)+1$	-191650245	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*5\wedge 3)/(2+1)$
-182452243	$9*(-8\wedge 7*(6+5-4/3)-2)-1$	-191650254	$-9-(8+7\wedge 6*5\wedge 3)*(2+1)$
-184319991	$-9*(8\wedge (-7/6)/5)\wedge -4*(3-21)$	-191650272	$(9+8+7\wedge 6*5\wedge 3)*(-2-1)$
-184320009	$-9+(8\wedge (-7/6)/5)\wedge -4*(3-21)$	-191650437	$(9*8+7\wedge 6*5\wedge 3)*(-2-1)$
-185165022	$-98*(7*(6\wedge 5+4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$	-192003159	$9-8*7\wedge 6*(5*(43-2)-1)$
-185165218	$-98*(7*(6\wedge 5+4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$	-192935135	$(9-8*7\wedge 6/5)*(4\wedge (3+2)+1)$
-186384375	$-9*(8\wedge 7\wedge 6-5)*4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1$	-192944343	$9-8*(7\wedge 6*5*(43-2)-1)$
-186450841	$(-9*8+7\wedge 6*5)*(4-321)$	-192944359	$9-8*(7\wedge 6*5*(43-2)+1)$
-186468276	$(-9-8+7\wedge 6*5)*(4-321)$	-192953585	$(-9-8*7\wedge 6/5)*(4\wedge (3+2)+1)$
-186471120	$9-(8-7\wedge 6*5)*(4-321)$	-193709900	$((9\wedge 8-76)*(-5-4)+3)/2+1$
-186471138	$-9-(8-7\wedge 6*5)*(4-321)$	-193709902	$((9\wedge 8-76)*(-5-4)+3)/2-1$
-186473348	$(-9+8+7\wedge 6*5)*(4-321)$	-193709903	$((9\wedge 8-76)*(-5-4)-3)/2+1$
-186473593	$9*8+7\wedge 6*5*(4-321)$	-193709905	$((9\wedge 8-76)*(-5-4)-3)/2-1$
-186473648	$9+8+7\wedge 6*5*(4-321)$	-193710584	$((9\wedge 8+76)*(-5-4)+3)/2+1$
-186473664	$9-8+7\wedge 6*5*(4-321)$	-193710586	$((9\wedge 8+76)*(-5-4)+3)/2-1$
-186473666	$-9+8+7\wedge 6*5*(4-321)$	-193710587	$((9\wedge 8+76)*(-5-4)-3)/2+1$
-186473682	$-9-8+7\wedge 6*5*(4-321)$	-193710589	$((9\wedge 8+76)*(-5-4)-3)/2-1$
-186473737	$-9*8+7\wedge 6*5*(4-321)$	-193767831	$9*(8-7\wedge 6*(5\wedge 3+21))$
-186473982	$(9-8+7\wedge 6*5)*(4-321)$	-193767975	$-9*(8+7\wedge 6*(5\wedge 3+21))$
-186476192	$9+(8+7\wedge 6*5)*(4-321)$	-194826599	$9*8*(7\wedge 6*(-5\wedge 4-3)+2)+1$
-186476210	$-9+(8+7\wedge 6*5)*(4-321)$	-194826601	$9*8*(7\wedge 6*(-5\wedge 4-3)+2)-1$
-186479054	$(9+8+7\wedge 6*5)*(4-321)$	-194826725	$-9*(8/(7\wedge 6-6/(5\wedge 4+3)))-2)+1$
-186496489	$(9*8+7\wedge 6*5)*(4-321)$	-194826727	$-9*(8/(7\wedge 6-6/(5\wedge 4+3)))-2)-1$
-187167229	$(9+8)*(7*6*(5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$	-194826761	$-9*(8/(7\wedge 6-6/(5\wedge 4+3)))+2)+1$
-187174369	$(-9-8)*(7*6*(5+4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$	-194826763	$-9*(8/(7\wedge 6-6/(5\wedge 4+3)))+2)-1$
-187174403	$(-9-8)*(7*6*(5+4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$	-194826887	$9*8*(7\wedge 6*(-5\wedge 4-3)-2)+1$
-188218674	$(-9*87+65)*(4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1)$	-194826889	$9*8*(7\wedge 6*(-5\wedge 4-3)-2)-1$
-188220110	$(-9*87+65)*(4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1)$	-196001176	$-98*(7\wedge 6*(5\wedge 4-3)-21)$
-188238310	$(9-8/7\wedge 6*5*4)*(3\wedge 2+1)$	-196002940	$-98*(7\wedge 6*(5\wedge 4-3)-2-1)$
-188238490	$(-9-8/7\wedge 6*5*4)*(3\wedge 2+1)$	-196003185	$-98*(7\wedge 6*(5\wedge 4-3)-2\wedge -1)$
-188825344	$9+8-(7\wedge 6*5-4)*321$	-196003217	$(-9-8)*(7\wedge (6-5+4+3)*2-1)$
-188825360	$9-8-(7\wedge 6*5-4)*321$	-196003251	$(-9-8)*(7\wedge (6-5+4+3)*2+1)$
-188825362	$-9+8-(7\wedge 6*5-4)*321$	-196005292	$-98*(7\wedge 6*(5\wedge 4-3)+21)$
-188825378	$-9-8-(7\wedge 6*5-4)*321$	-196082964	$(9+8-765)*(4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1)$
-188827912	$9+8-(7\wedge 6*5+4)*321$	-196084460	$(9+8-765)*(4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1)$
-188827928	$9-8-(7\wedge 6*5+4)*321$	-196942194	$(9*8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4)*(32-1)$
-188827930	$-9+8-(7\wedge 6*5+4)*321$	-196943899	$(9+8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4)*(32-1)$
-188827946	$-9-8-(7\wedge 6*5+4)*321$	-196944169	$9+(8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4)*(32-1)$
-189035532	$(-98*7\wedge 6/54\wedge 3)\wedge (-2+1)$	-196944187	$-9+(8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4)*(32-1)$
-190238335	$98*(7\wedge 6*(5-43/2)+1)$	-196944354	$9*8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4*(32-1)$
-190238531	$98*(7\wedge 6*(5-43/2)-1)$	-196944395	$(9-8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4)*(32-1)$
-191041893	$(9\wedge 8-(7-65)\wedge 4\wedge 3)*-21$	-196944409	$9+8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4*(32-1)$
-191099322	$9*((87-6)*(5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$	-196944425	$9-8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4*(32-1)$
-191099340	$9*((87-6)*(5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$	-196944427	$-9+8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4*(32-1)$
-191103777	$-9*(8+(7\wedge 6+5)*(4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1))$	-196944443	$-9-8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4*(32-1)$
-191106612	$-9*((87-6)*(5+4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$	-196944457	$(9-8+7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4)*(-32+1)$
-191156225	$(9*8-7\wedge 6*5)*(4+321)$	-196944498	$9*-8-7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4*(32-1)$
-191174100	$(9+8-7\wedge 6*5)*(4+321)$	-196944665	$9-(8+7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4)*(32-1)$
-191177016	$9+(8-7\wedge 6*5)*(4+321)$	-196944683	$-9-(8+7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4)*(32-1)$
-191177034	$-9+(8-7\wedge 6*5)*(4+321)$	-196944953	$(9+8+7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4)*(-32+1)$
-191179300	$(9-8-7\wedge 6*5)*(4+321)$	-196946658	$(9*8+7\wedge 6*5\wedge 4)*(-32+1)$
-191179553	$9*8-7\wedge 6*5*(4+321)$	-198177075	$9*((8+76)*(5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)+1)$
-191179608	$9+8-7\wedge 6*5*(4+321)$	-198177093	$9*((8+76)*(5-4\wedge 3\wedge 2)-1)$
-191179624	$9-8-7\wedge 6*5*(4+321)$	-198442242	$9+(8-765)*(4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1)$
-191179626	$-9+8-7\wedge 6*5*(4+321)$	-198442260	$-9+(8-765)*(4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1)$
-191179642	$-9-8-7\wedge 6*5*(4+321)$	-198442998	$9+(8-765)*4\wedge 3\wedge 2+1$
-191179697	$9*-8-7\wedge 6*5*(4+321)$	-198443000	$9+(8-765)*4\wedge 3\wedge 2-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-198443016	$-9+(8-765)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-203415122	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*32+1)$
-198443018	$-9+(8-765)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-203415138	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*32+1)$
-198443756	$9+(8-765)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-203415193	$9^*-8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*32+1)$
-198443774	$-9+(8-765)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-203885619	$98-7^{\wedge}6^*(5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-199170135	$9^*(87^*(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-203885645	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-199170153	$9^*(87^*(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-203885789	$9^*-8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-200003283	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4^*(3+2)-1)$	-203885815	$-98-7^{\wedge}6^*(5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$
-200003291	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-203901552	$9^*87^*-6^*((5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-200003317	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^*4^*(3+2)+1)$	-203905467	$9^*87^*(-6^*(5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-200120454	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4)-3)^*21)$	-203905719	$9-87^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-200121444	$9^*(8-(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4)+3)^*21)$	-203905737	$-9-87^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-200121588	$-9^*(8+(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4)+3)^*21)$	-203906154	$9-87^*(6^*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-200277252	$(9-8-765)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-203906172	$-9-87^*(6^*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-200278780	$(9-8-765)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-203906328	$9-87^*(6^*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-200473879	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43-2)-1)$	-203906346	$-9-87^*(6^*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-200473895	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43-2)+1)$	-203906763	$9-87^*6^*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-200473897	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43-2)-1)$	-203907033	$9^*-87^*(6^*(5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-200539323	$9^*8-765^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-204238647	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43+2)-1)$
-200539378	$9+8-765^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-204238663	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43+2)+1)$
-200539394	$9-8-765^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-204709251	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-200539396	$-9+8-765^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-205136226	$9^{\wedge}8^*(-7+(6/5/4^*3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$
-200539412	$-9-8-765^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-205207074	$9^*87^*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-200539467	$-9^*8-765^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-205207848	$9^*(87^*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-200540853	$9^*8-765^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-205207856	$9^*87^*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-200540908	$9+8-765^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-205207858	$9^*87^*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-200540924	$9-8-765^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-205207866	$9^*(87^*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-200540926	$-9+8-765^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-205208640	$9^*87^*(65-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-200540942	$-9-8-765^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-205235253	$9^*(87^*(6^*5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-200540997	$-9^*8-765^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-205250130	$9^*(87^*(6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-200801538	$(-9+8-765)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-205250148	$9^*(87^*(6+5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-200803070	$(-9+8-765)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-205257960	$9^*(87^*(6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-200881128	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)^*(-4-(3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-205257978	$9^*(87^*(6-5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-200888268	$(9^{\wedge}8+765)^*(-4-(3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-205282233	$-9^*(87^*(6^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-201767937	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4+3)/2-1)$	-205282251	$-9^*(87^*(6^*5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-201767963	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-205308864	$-9^*87^*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-201768107	$9^*-8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4+3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-205309638	$-9^*(87^*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-201768133	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(4+3)/2+1)$	-205309646	$-9^*87^*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-201770433	$-9^{\wedge}8^*(7^*6^{\wedge}-5^*(4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-205309648	$-9^*87^*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-201885675	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-205309656	$-9^*(87^*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-202356267	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^*43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-205310430	$-9^*87^*(65+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-202356275	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-205415082	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43-21))$
-202356285	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^*43-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-205415226	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43-21))$
-202636530	$9-(8+765)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-207062231	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6^*5^*(43+2-1)$
-202636548	$-9-(8+765)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-207532542	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4/3-2-1)$
-202637302	$9-(8+765)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-207532639	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4/3-2)+1$
-202637304	$9-(8+765)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-207532640	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4/3-2)^{\wedge}1$
-202637320	$-9-(8+765)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1$	-207532641	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4/3-2)-1$
-202637322	$-9-(8+765)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$	-207532738	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4/3-2+1)$
-202638076	$9-(8+765)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-207532787	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4/3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-202638094	$-9-(8+765)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-207532885	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4/3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-202709129	$98+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-207532934	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4/3+2-1)$
-202709155	$9^*8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-207533031	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4/3+2)+1$
-202709299	$9^*-8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-207533032	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4/3+2)^{\wedge}1$
-202709325	$-98+7^{\wedge}6^*(5-(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-207533033	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4/3+2)-1$
-202826867	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-207533130	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4/3+2+1)$
-203179751	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-207533326	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4)+3)^*2-1)$
-203179806	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-208084959	$9^{\wedge}8^*-7+65^{\wedge}4/3/(2+1)$
-203179822	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-208090701	$-9^*(87+6/5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-203179824	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-209453039	$(-9-8)^*((7^*6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-203179840	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-209453073	$(-9-8)^*((7^*6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-203179895	$9^*-8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-209648142	$(9^*8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4)^*(32+1)$
-203204160	$-9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*(3+21)$	-209649957	$(9+8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4)^*(32+1)$
-203285808	$-9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*(3+21)$	-209650245	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4)^*(32+1)$
-203288734	$98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-209650263	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4)^*(32+1)$
-203288930	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-209650446	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4^*(32+1)$
-203306014	$98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-209650485	$(9-8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4)^*(32+1)$
-203306210	$-98-(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-209650501	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4^*(32+1)$
-203309136	$-9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*(3+21)$	-209650517	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4^*(32+1)$
-203390784	$-9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*(3+21)$	-209650519	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4^*(32+1)$
-203415049	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43+2^{\wedge}+1)$	-209650535	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4^*(32+1)$
-203415104	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43+2^{\wedge}+1)$	-209650551	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4)^*(-32-1)$
-203415120	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^*43+2^{\wedge}+1)$	-209650590	$9^*-8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^{\wedge}4^*(32+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-209650773	$9 - (8+7^6*54)*(32+1)$	-223062602	$-98 - 7^6*(5^4*3+21)$
-209650791	$-9 - (8+7^6*54)*(32+1)$	-223077663	$9 - (8+7^6)*(5^4*3+21)$
-209651079	$(9+8+7^6*54)*(-32-1)$	-223077681	$-9 - (8+7^6)*(5^4*3+21)$
-209652894	$(9*8+7^6*54)*(-32-1)$	-223248312	$(98+7^6)*(5^4*3-21)$
-209988114	$(-9-8)*(7^6*5-43)*21$	-225533052	$9*(8-7^6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$
-210018816	$(-9-8)*(7^6*5+43)*21$	-225533196	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4*3-2)-1)$
-210486874	$9^8-7^6*5*(432-1)$	-225533214	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4*3-2)+1)$
-210659722	$-98*(7+6/5)*(4^3*2+1)$	-225885648	$(9-8*7^6*5)*((4+3)^2-1)$
-211347351	$9*(-87*(6^5+4^3*2)+1)$	-225886512	$(-9-8*7^6*5)*((4+3)^2-1)$
-211347369	$9*(-87*(6^5+4^3*2)-1)$	-225967266	$(9-876+5)*(4^3*2-1)$
-211663364	$9^8-7^6*5*(432+1)$	-225968990	$(9-876+5)*(4^3*2+1)$
-212709383	$9-8*7^6*5*(43+2)+1$	-226591902	$9*(8-7^6*(5^4*3-2+1))$
-213978383	$-9/(8/((7^6-5^4)/3))^2+1$	-226592046	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4*3-2+1))$
-213978385	$-9/(8/((7^6-5^4)/3))^2-1$	-227273646	$(-9+876)*(5-4^3*2+1)$
-215032904	$-9-(8*(7^6-5^4*3))^2+1$	-227275380	$(-9+876)*(5-4^3*2-1)$
-215032906	$-9-(8*(7^6-5^4*3))^2-1$	-227282316	$(9-876)*(5+4^3*2-1)$
-216003492	$-9*8*(7^6*(54-3)/2-1)$	-227284050	$(9-876)*(5+4^3*2+1)$
-216003636	$-9*8*(7^6*(54-3)/2+1)$	-227647530	$9*((8-7^6*5)*43+21)$
-216414585	$9^8*((-7-6)/(5+4))^3*2+1$	-227647692	$9*((8-7^6*5)*43+2+1)$
-216474151	$9-8*7^6*5*(43+2+1)$	-227647710	$9*((8-7^6*5)*43+2-1)$
-217059444	$9*((8-7^6*5)*(43-2)+1)$	-227647728	$9*((8-7^6*5)*43-2+1)$
-217059462	$9*((8-7^6*5)*(43-2)-1)$	-227647746	$9*((8-7^6*5)*43-2-1)$
-217062468	$-9*(8+7^6*5*(43-2)-1)$	-227647908	$9*((8-7^6*5)*43-21)$
-217062486	$-9*(8+7^6*5*(43-2)+1)$	-227650554	$9*(8-7^6*5*43+21)$
-218452396	$(9-8^7)/6/5^4-4-(3*2)^{-1}$	-227650698	$-9*(8+7^6*5*43-21)$
-219410334	$9*((87+6)*(5-4^3*2)+1)$	-227650716	$9*(8-7^6*5*43+2+1)$
-219410352	$9*((87+6)*(5-4^3*2)-1)$	-227650722	$9*(8-7^6*5*43)+21$
-219413691	$(-9*8-765)*(4^3*2-1)$	-227650764	$9*(8-7^6*5*43)-21$
-219415365	$(-9*8-765)*(4^3*2+1)$	-227650860	$-9*(8+7^6*5*43-2-1)$
-219532936	$98-7^6*(5^4*3)*(2+1)$	-227650866	$-9*(8+7^6*5*43)+21$
-219533132	$-98-7^6*(5^4*3)*(2+1)$	-227650878	$-9*(8+7^6*5*43-2+1)$
-220069070	$9*(8-7*(6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	-227650896	$-9*(8+7^6*5*43+2-1)$
-220069072	$9*(8-7*(6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	-227650908	$-9*(8+7^6*5*43)-21$
-220069214	$9*(8+7*(6-5^4*3)^2)+1$	-227650914	$-9*(8+7^6*5*43+2+1)$
-220069216	$-9*(8+7*(6-5^4*3)^2)-1$	-227650932	$9*(8-7^6*5*43-21)$
-220238830	$98-7^6*(5^4*3-2-1)$	-227651076	$-9*(8+7^6*5*43+21)$
-220239026	$-98-7^6*(5^4*3-2-1)$	-227653722	$-9*((8+7^6*5)*43-21)$
-220474128	$98-7^6*(5^4*3-2+1)$	-227653884	$-9*((8+7^6*5)*43-2-1)$
-220474154	$9*8-7^6*(5^4*3-2+1)$	-227654100	$-9*((8+7^6*5)*43+21)$
-220474298	$9*-8-7^6*(5^4*3-2+1)$	-228326544	$9-(876-5)*(4^3*2-1)$
-220474324	$-98-7^6*(5^4*3-2+1)$	-228326562	$-9-(876-5)*(4^3*2-1)$
-220577686	$9*((8-7^6)*5^4/3+21)$	-228327414	$9-(876-5)*4^3*2+1$
-220577064	$9*((8-7^6)*5^4/3-21)$	-228327416	$9-(876-5)*4^3*2-1$
-220606686	$9*((8+7^6)*5^4/-3+21)$	-228327432	$-9-(876-5)*4^3*2+1$
-220607064	$9*((8+7^6)*5^4/-3-21)$	-228327434	$-9-(876-5)*4^3*2-1$
-220607793	$(9^8+(7-65^4)*3)*21$	-228328286	$9-(876-5)*(4^3*2+1)$
-220608675	$(9^8-(7+65^4)*3)*21$	-228328304	$-9-(876-5)*(4^3*2+1)$
-220709426	$98-7^6*(5^4*3+2-1)$	-228588696	$(9-876-5)*(4^3*2-1)$
-220709452	$9*8-7^6*(5^4*3+2-1)$	-228590440	$(9-876-5)*(4^3*2+1)$
-220709596	$9*-8-7^6*(5^4*3+2-1)$	-228709476	$-9*8*((7^6*5-4-3)/2-1)$
-220709622	$-98-7^6*(5^4*3+2-1)$	-228709539	$-9*(8*(7^6*5-4-3)/2-1)$
-220944724	$98-7^6*(5^4*3+2+1)$	-228709557	$-9*(8*(7^6*5-4-3)/2+1)$
-220944750	$9*8-7^6*(5^4*3+2+1)$	-228709755	$-9*(8*(7^6*5+3)/2-1)$
-220944894	$9*-8-7^6*(5^4*3+2+1)$	-228709773	$-9*(8*(7^6*5+3)/2+1)$
-220944920	$-98-7^6*(5^4*3+2+1)$	-228709836	$-9*8*((7^6*5+3)/2+1)$
-221374701	$-9^8(-8+7+6)*(5^4*3^2-1)$	-228944954	$-98*7^6*(5^4*3/21)$
-221492799	$-9^8(-8+7+6)*(5^4*3^2+1)$	-229632879	$9+876*(5-4^3*2+1)$
-221650618	$98-7^6*(5^4+3)*(2+1)$	-229632897	$-9+876*(5-4^3*2+1)$
-221650814	$-98-7^6*(5^4+3)*(2+1)$	-229633754	$9+876*(5-4^3*2)+1$
-222297264	$(-9*87-65)*(4^3*2-1)$	-229633756	$9+876*(5-4^3*2)-1$
-222298960	$(-9*87-65)*(4^3*2+1)$	-229633772	$-9+876*(5-4^3*2)+1$
-222356610	$-98*7^6*5*(4-3/21)$	-229633774	$-9+876*(5-4^3*2)-1$
-222356682	$-9*(8+7^6*5*(43-2+1))$	-229634631	$9+876*(5-4^3*2-1)$
-222876696	$(98-7^6)*(5^4*3+21)$	-229634649	$-9+876*(5-4^3*2-1)$
-222904070	$9*(8-7*(6+5^4*3)^2)+1$	-229641639	$9-876*(5+4^3*2-1)$
-222904072	$9*(8-7*(6+5^4*3)^2)-1$	-229641657	$-9-876*(5+4^3*2-1)$
-222904214	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^4*3)^2)+1$	-229642514	$9-876*(5+4^3*2)+1$
-222904216	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^4*3)^2)-1$	-229642516	$9-876*(5+4^3*2)-1$
-222985091	$9*8*(7/6-54)^3*21$	-229642532	$-9-876*(5+4^3*2)+1$
-223047327	$9+(8-7^6)*(5^4*3+21)$	-229642534	$-9-876*(5+4^3*2)-1$
-223047345	$-9+(8-7^6)*(5^4*3+21)$	-229643391	$9-876*(5+4^3*2+1)$
-223062406	$98-7^6*(5^4*3+21)$	-229643409	$-9-876*(5+4^3*2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-229686226	$98^*(7-6*(5^4\wedge(3/2)-1))$	-237499401	$-9-8*76*(5^4\wedge(3/2)-1)$
-229686716	$98^*(7-6*5^4\wedge(3/2)+1)$	-237499983	$9-8*(76*5^4\wedge(3/2)-1)$
-229687598	$-98^*(7+6*(5^4\wedge(3/2)-1))$	-237499999	$9-8*(76*5^4\wedge(3/2)+1)$
-229688088	$-98^*(7+6*5^4\wedge(3/2)-1)$	-237500001	$-9-8*(76*5^4\wedge(3/2)-1)$
-229688284	$-98^*(7+6*5^4\wedge(3/2)+1)$	-237500017	$-9-8*(76*5^4\wedge(3/2)+1)$
-229688774	$-98^*(7+6*(5^4\wedge(3/2)+1))$	-237500599	$9-8*76*(5^4\wedge(3/2)+1)$
-229768560	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4+3)-1)$	-238235976	$9*((8-7^6*5)^*(43+2)+1)$
-229768578	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4+3)+1)$	-238235994	$9*((8-7^6*5)^*(43+2)-1)$
-230582142	$-98^*((7^6-5)^4*(3+2)-1)$	-238242456	$-9*((8+7^6*5)^*(43+2)-1)$
-230588806	$-98^*(7^6*5^4-32-1)$	-238262892	$98^*(-7^6+5^4*3)*21$
-230589002	$-98^*(7^6*5^4-32+1)$	-238550130	$-98/7*65*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-230589394	$-98^*(7^6*5^4-3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-238551026	$-98/7*(65*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-230591060	$98^*(7^6*5^4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-238551054	$-98/7*(65*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-230591256	$98^*(7^6*5^4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-238551950	$-98/7*65*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-230591697	$-98^*(7^6*5^4-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-239163741	$9-((8+7)^6-5^4*3)*21$
-230592026	$-98^*(7^6*5^4-3/21)$	-239163759	$-9-((8+7)^6-5^4*3)*21$
-230592054	$-98^*(7^6*5^4+3/21)$	-239197041	$9+(8+7)^6*(5^{\wedge}-4/3-21)$
-230592089	$-98^*(7^6*5^4+3/2-1)$	-239197059	$-9+(8+7)^6*(5^{\wedge}5^{\wedge}-4/3-21)$
-230592824	$-98^*(7^6*5^4+3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-239198741	$9-((8+7)^6-5^4/3)*21$
-230593020	$-98^*(7^6*5^4+3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-239198759	$-9-((8+7)^6-5^4/3)*21$
-230594686	$-98^*(7^6*5^4+3^{\wedge}(2+1))$	-239207491	$9-((8+7)^6+5^4/3)*21$
-230595078	$-98^*(7^6*5^4+32-1)$	-239207509	$-9-((8+7)^6+5^4/3)*21$
-230595274	$-98^*(7^6*5^4+32+1)$	-239209191	$9-(8+7)^6*(5^{\wedge}-4/3+21)$
-230685840	$(-9-876+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-239209209	$-9-(8+7)^6*(5^{\wedge}-4/3+21)$
-230687600	$(-9-876+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-239242491	$9-((8+7)^6+5^4*3)*21$
-230827266	$9*(8-7^6*(5^4+3+2+1))$	-239242509	$-9-((8+7)^6+5^4*3)*21$
-230827410	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4+3+2+1))$	-239257791	$9-(8+7)^6*(5^{\wedge}-4*3+21)$
-230947974	$9-(876+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-239257809	$-9-(8+7)^6*(5^{\wedge}-4*3+21)$
-230947992	$9-(876+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-239297994	$9*(8-7^6*(5^4*(43+2)+1))$
-230948854	$9-(876+5)^*4^3\wedge 2+1$	-239298138	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4*(43+2)+1))$
-230948856	$9-(876+5)^*4^3\wedge 2-1$	-240003943	$(-9-8)*(7^6*5^4*3^2-1)$
-230948872	$9-(876+5)^*4^3\wedge 2+1$	-240003977	$(-9-8)*(7^6*5^4*3^2+1)$
-230948874	$9-(876+5)^*4^3\wedge 2-1$	-240742773	$9^8*(76/54-3^2-1)$
-230949736	$9-(876+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-240983361	$9*((8+7-65^4*3)/2+1)$
-230949754	$-9-(876+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-240983514	$-9*((8+7+65^4*3)/2+1)$
-231992130	$(9+876)^*(5-4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-241415676	$-9*8*(7^6*(5+3)/2-1)$
-231993900	$(9+876)^*(5-4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-241415739	$-9*(8*7^6*(5+3)/2-1)$
-232000980	$(-9-876)^*(5+4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-241415820	$-9*8*(7^6*(5+3)/2+1)$
-232002750	$(-9-876)^*(5+4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-241692892	$-98*(7^6-5^4/3)*21$
-232239126	$-98*7^6*(5^4+3/21)$	-242550392	$-98*(7^6+5^4/3)*21$
-232421858	$(9+8)^*(7*(-6+5-4)^3\wedge 2+1)$	-243533358	$9*(8-7^6*5^4*(43+2+1))$
-232421892	$(9+8)^*(7*(-6+5-4)^3\wedge 2-1)$	-243533502	$-9*(8+7^6*5^4*(43+2+1))$
-232783853	$9*(-8^7*(6+5+4/3)+2)+1$	-245980392	$-98*(7^6+5^4*3)*21$
-232783855	$9*(-8^7*(6+5+4/3)+2)-1$	-246004042	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5-4^3*2)+1)$
-232783889	$-9*(8^7*(6+5+4/3)+2)+1$	-247875810	$-98*((7^6-5)^4*3/2-1)$
-232783891	$-9*(8^7*(6+5+4/3)+2)-1$	-247876006	$-98*((7^6-5)^4*3/2+1)$
-233307270	$(-9-876-5)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-247886345	$-98*(7^6*(5^4+3/2)-1)$
-233309050	$(-9-876-5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-247896880	$-98*((7^6+5)^4*3/2-1)$
-233886212	$98*7^6*(5/(4+3)-21)$	-247897076	$-98*((7^6+5)^4*3/2+1)$
-234365460	$9^8*(76/(5+4)+3)+21$	-250870842	$9-87*(6+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-234365502	$9^8*(76/(5+4)+3)-21$	-250871712	$9-87*((6+5)^4*3\wedge 2-1)$
-235192904	$-9*(8*(7^6+5^4*3))^2+1$	-250871886	$9-87*((6+5)^4*3\wedge 2+1)$
-235192906	$-9*(8*(7^6+5^4*3))^2-1$	-250872756	$9-87*(6+5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-235297550	$(9-8*7^6*5)*((4+3)^2+1)$	-252042328	$9^8*7-65^4*(32-1)$
-235298450	$(-9-8*7^6*5)*((4+3)^2+1)$	-252611622	$9^8*(7+6^{\wedge}-5^4\wedge(3+2)+1)$
-235605510	$9^8*(7+6^{\wedge}-5^4\wedge(3^2)+1)$	-253180639	$9-8*7^6*(54*(3+2)-1)$
-236003877	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5-4^3)*2+1)$	-253502563	$(9*8-7^6*5)^*(432-1)$
-236003911	$(9+8)^*(7^6*(5-4^3)*2-1)$	-253526268	$(9+8-7^6*5)^*(432-1)$
-236346796	$-98*(7^6-5)^*(43/2-1)$	-253530138	$9+(8-7^6*5)^*(432-1)$
-236366886	$-98*(7^6+5)^*(43/2-1)$	-253530156	$-9+(8-7^6*5)^*(432-1)$
-236715843	$(9-8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)^4*3)*21$	-253533164	$(9-8-7^6*5)^*(432-1)$
-236716221	$(9+8^{\wedge}(7-6+5)^4*3)*-21$	-253533523	$9*8-7^6*5*(432-1)$
-236727441	$9^8*((-7-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)/2+1)$	-253533578	$9+8-7^6*5*(432-1)$
-236786490	$9^8*((7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)/-2+1)$	-253533594	$9-8-7^6*5*(432-1)$
-237170232	$9*8*((7^6-5)^*(4-32)+1)$	-253533596	$-9+8-7^6*5*(432-1)$
-237170295	$9*(8*(7^6-5)^*(4-32)+1)$	-253533612	$-9-8-7^6*5*(432-1)$
-237170376	$9*8*((7^6-5)^*(4-32)-1)$	-253533667	$9*-8-7^6*5*(432-1)$
-237180375	$9-8*7^6*(5+4+3)*21$	-253534026	$(9-8+7^6*5)^*(-432+1)$
-237190392	$9*8*((7^6+5)^*(4-32)+1)$	-253537034	$9-(8+7^6*5)^*(432-1)$
-237190455	$9*(8*(7^6+5)^*(4-32)+1)$	-253537052	$-9-(8+7^6*5)^*(432-1)$
-237190536	$9*8*((7^6+5)^*(4-32)-1)$	-253540922	$(9+8+7^6*5)^*(-432+1)$
-237499383	$9-8*76*(5^4\wedge(3/2)-1)$	-253564627	$(9*8+7^6*5)^*(-432+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-254004174	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*432-1)$	-267186744	$9*(8-76*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1))$
-254004190	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*432-1)$	-267186888	$-9*(8+76*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1))$
-254004192	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*432-1)$	-267187419	$9*(8-76*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-254004208	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*432-1)$	-267187563	$-9*(8+76*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-254239472	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*432+1)$	-267187581	$-9*(8+76*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-254239488	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*432+1)$	-267188256	$-9*(8+76*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1))$
-254239490	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*432+1)$	-267964536	$98*(7*(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))+1)$
-254239506	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*432+1)$	-267964732	$98*(7*(6-5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1)$
-254501190	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+(6/(5+4)))^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$	-267972768	$-98*(7*(6+5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2))-1)$
-254592427	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6*(543/2-1)$	-268435420	$(9-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^4)*(3+2-1)$
-254592445	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(543/2-1)$	-268435492	$(9+8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^4)*(-3-2+1)$
-254671047	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6*5*4*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-270122095	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*((5+4)*32-1)$
-254678909	$(9*8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	-270883287	$9*((-8*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32+1)$
-254702724	$(9+8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	-270883305	$9*((-8*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32-1)$
-254706612	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	-270938808	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*32-1)$
-254706630	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	-270938871	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*32-1)$
-254709652	$(9-8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	-270938889	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*32+1)$
-254710013	$9*8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(432+1)$	-270938952	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-54)*32+1)$
-254710068	$9+8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(432+1)$	-271042551	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*32-1)$
-254710084	$9-8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(432+1)$	-271042632	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*32+1)$
-254710086	$-9+8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(432+1)$	-271047735	$-9*((8*7^{\wedge}6-54)*32-1)$
-254710102	$-9-8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(432+1)$	-271052919	$-9*((8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)+4)*32-1)$
-254710157	$9*-8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(432+1)$	-271062927	$-9*((8*7^{\wedge}6-5/4)*32-1)$
-254710518	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(-432-1)$	-271066167	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32-1)$
-254713540	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	-271066248	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5/4)*32+1)$
-254713558	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(432+1)$	-271078839	$-9*((8*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32-1)$
-254717446	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(-432-1)$	-271078857	$-9*((8*7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32+1)$
-254741261	$(9*8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(-432-1)$	-271187640	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32-1)$
-254802753	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-271187703	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32-1)$
-254805183	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5-4^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-271187721	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32+1)$
-255063023	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(54*(3+2)+1)$	-271187784	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32+1)$
-255393783	$9*(8^{\wedge}7*(6-5^{\wedge}4/32)+1)$	-271243287	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32-1)$
-255393801	$9*(8^{\wedge}7*(6-5^{\wedge}4/32)-1)$	-271243305	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32+1)$
-255533611	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*543/2-1)$	-272503224	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32-1)$
-255533627	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*543/2+1)$	-272503287	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32-1)$
-255533629	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*543/2-1)$	-272503305	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32+1)$
-255533645	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*543/2+1)$	-272503368	$-9*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*32+1)$
-255589416	$9-(8+7)*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-272628912	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+6/(5+4))+321$
-255590376	$9-(8+7)*(65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-272629554	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+6/(5+4))-321$
-255590406	$9-(8+7)*(65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-274060800	$-9*8*((76+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-255591366	$9-(8+7)*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-274060944	$-9*8*((76+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-255993327	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^4*3*2-1)$	-275498879	$((9^{\wedge}8-7+6)/-5+4)*32+1$
-256474811	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(543/2+1)$	-275498881	$((9^{\wedge}8-7+6)/-5+4)*32-1$
-256474829	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(543/2+1)$	-275499135	$((9^{\wedge}8-7+6)/-5-4)*32+1$
-257160582	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+(6/(5+4)))^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-275499137	$((9^{\wedge}8-7+6)/-5-4)*32-1$
-258279423	$9^{\wedge}8*(7+6-5)+43*21$	-276004537	$(-9-8)*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)*2-1)$
-258281229	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+6-5)-43*21$	-276004571	$(-9-8)*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)*2+1)$
-259400070	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7+(6/(5+4)))^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-276251839	$((9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6)/-5+4)*32+1$
-259405020	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43/2+1)$	-276251841	$((9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6)/-5+4)*32-1$
-259427070	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(43/2+1)$	-276252095	$((9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6)/-5-4)*32+1$
-260474877	$9*(8*7^{\wedge}6*(5/4-32)+1)$	-276252097	$((9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6)/-5-4)*32-1$
-261060313	$(9+8)/(-7/((6^{\wedge}5*4/3)^{\wedge}2-1))$	-276479757	$(9-(8^{\wedge}(7/-6)/5)^{\wedge}4)*3^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-262059462	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7+(6/(5+4)))^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	-276480243	$(9+(8^{\wedge}(7/-6)/5)^{\wedge}4)/-3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-262472040	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(32-1)$	-276710350	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+43)/2-1)$
-262607634	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+54)*(32-1)$	-278004570	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-262713096	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(32-1)$	-278004604	$(9+8)*7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-263949030	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-6^{\wedge}-5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-278906233	$(-9-8)*7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-264201768	$9-(8^{\wedge}7*6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	-278906267	$(-9-8)*7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-264201786	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7*6-5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	-279405720	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6-54)*(32+1)$
-264236768	$9-(8^{\wedge}7*6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	-279517986	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6-54)*(32+1)$
-264236786	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7*6-5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	-279550062	$-9*(8*7^{\wedge}6+54)*(32+1)$
-264245518	$9-(8^{\wedge}7*6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	-279662328	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6+54)*(32+1)$
-264245536	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7*6+5^{\wedge}4/3)*21$	-280955142	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-6^{\wedge}-5*4^{\wedge}(3*2)+1)$
-264280518	$9-(8^{\wedge}7*6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	-281416399	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-21)$
-264280536	$-9-(8^{\wedge}7*6+5^{\wedge}4*3)*21$	-281416417	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-21)$
-265178788	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)-21)$	-281651634	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5/4+32)-1)$
-265182904	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5*4+3)+21)$	-281651778	$-9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5/4+32)+1)$
-266004372	$(-9-8)*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3*2)-1)$	-282590840	$-98*(7+(6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-266004406	$(-9-8)*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3*2)+1)$	-282591820	$-98*(7+(6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-266251941	$9^{\wedge}8*(7/((6/5/4-3)/2)-1)$	-282592016	$-98*(7+(6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-266827860	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4+3)*21)$	-282592996	$-98*(7+(6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-266828004	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4+3)*21)$	-283056849	$9^{\wedge}8*((-76/54)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-284828157	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54*(3+2)-1))$	-301206797	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+65*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$
-284828301	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54*(3+2)-1))$	-301206927	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+65*(43^{\wedge}2-1)$
-285886701	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6*54)*(3+2)+1)$	-301231041	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3*2+1)$
-285886719	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6*54)*(3+2)-1)$	-301231053	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3*2-1)$
-285886989	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54*(3+2)+1)$	-301239687	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+65*4^{\wedge}3*21$
-285887133	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(3+2)-1)$	-301267977	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+(6/54)^{\wedge}3)+21$
-285887151	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(3+2)+1)$	-301268019	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+(6/54)^{\wedge}3)-21$
-285887421	$-9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(3+2)-1)$	-301305441	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*((5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-286122359	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-321)$	-301305453	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*((5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-286122377	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-321)$	-301309713	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(5+4)*321$
-286945839	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(54*(3+2)+1))$	-301311738	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6/54)^{\wedge}-3*21$
-286945983	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(54*(3+2)+1))$	-301312923	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6+5)*4*321$
-287063011	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	-301314057	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*5*(432+1)$
-287064109	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2-1)$	-301314081	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(5^*432+1)$
-287743578	$9^{\wedge}8*7-65^{\wedge}4*(32+1)$	-301314093	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(5^*432-1)$
-287992495	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-301314117	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*5*(432-1)$
-287992529	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-301316133	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6^*5+4)*321$
-288016975	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-301316673	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(5^*432+1)$
-288017009	$(-9-8)*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-301316685	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(5^*432-1)$
-288053458	$-98*7*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-301317114	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6+5)*43*21$
-288054830	$-98*7*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-301317273	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*543*(2+1)$
-288241912	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*(3+2)-1)$	-301317297	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*5*(4+321)$
-289669103	$(-9-8)*((7+6)*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-301317537	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-6*5*(4-321)$
-290966815	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(654/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-301319373	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-6*(5-4*321)$
-291229668	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+(6/5/4^*3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$	-301319549	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-(6-54^{\wedge}3)/21$
-294004753	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)/2-1)$	-301320180	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6^*54+3)*21$
-294004949	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)/2+1)$	-301320306	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6^*54-3)*21$
-294590279	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6)*((5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$	-301320807	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+65*4*(3+21)$
-294595913	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6)*((5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$	-301321371	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(5^{\wedge}4+321)$
-295416567	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)*(32-1))$	-301321392	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+65*(43*2+1)$
-295416711	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)*(32-1))$	-301321522	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+65*(4^{\wedge}3+21)$
-296143047	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6^*5^*4)^{\wedge}3*(2+1)$	-301321524	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(65^*4+3)*21$
-296474913	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	-301321650	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(65^*4-3)*21$
-296476047	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	-301321815	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+654*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-296544015	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+6/54)+3*21$	-301322232	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6+5+4)*321$
-296544141	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+6/54)-3*21$	-301322284	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6+5)*(432+1)$
-296841240	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)*321$	-301322306	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6+5)*(432-1)$
-297960039	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6^{\wedge}5*(432+1)$	-301322367	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-65*4*(3-21)$
-297975591	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6^{\wedge}5*(432-1)$	-301322697	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*5*((4^*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-298004900	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-301323212	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-65*(4-3*21)$
-298004934	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4^*3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-301323472	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6+5)*(4+321)$
-298020177	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6+54^{\wedge}3)*21$	-301323783	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(543+2-1)$
-298020429	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-(6-54^{\wedge}3)*21$	-301323795	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(543-2+1)$
-298345175	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-321)$	-301324057	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+65*(43+2+1)$
-298345193	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-321)$	-301324187	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+65*(43-2-1)$
-298356270	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-321)$	-301324317	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+65*(43+2+1)$
-298356288	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-321)$	-301324338	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(65+4^{\wedge}3)*21$
-298359440	$9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-321)$	-301324419	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(5+432+1)$
-298359458	$-9+(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-321)$	-301324431	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+654*(3+2-1)$
-298370535	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-321)$	-301324479	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-6*(5-432-1)$
-298370553	$-9+8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-321)$	-301324491	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-6*(5-432+1)$
-298799847	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6^{\wedge}5*(4+321)$	-301324758	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+654*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-298862055	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-6^{\wedge}5*(4-321)$	-301324770	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(65+4)*(32+1)$
-299428407	$-9*((8-76^{\wedge}(-5+4+3))^{\wedge}2-1)$	-301324800	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6+5-4)*321$
-299557947	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(543^{\wedge}2+1)$	-301324908	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(65+4)*(32-1)$
-299557959	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(543^{\wedge}2-1)$	-301325034	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(65-4)*(32+1)$
-300382137	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(54^{\wedge}3+21)$	-301325223	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(5^{\wedge}4-321)$
-300382389	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(54^{\wedge}3-21)$	-301325241	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-6*(5^*4-321)$
-300517623	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*321$	-301325292	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-65*(4-32+1)$
-300517641	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*321$	-301325391	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(65+4)*(3+21)$
-300703023	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6^{\wedge}5/4*321$	-301325442	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6-5+4)*321$
-300946133	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5/4-321)$	-301325514	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6^*5+43)*21$
-300946151	$-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*(5/4-321)$	-301325559	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-(6-54)*(32-1)$
-301124496	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6+5^{\wedge}4)*321$	-301325631	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(5^*43+21)$
-301128348	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-(6-5^{\wedge}4)*321$	-301325654	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(65+4/3)*21$
-301132647	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6^{\wedge}5*(4^*3*2+1)$	-301325710	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(65-4/3)*21$
-301162848	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6^{\wedge}5+43)*21$	-301325883	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(5^*43-21)$
-301164654	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6^{\wedge}5-43)*21$	-301326123	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+(6-5+43)*21$
-301181263	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-301326453	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(5^*4*(3+2)-1)$
-301181281	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-301326537	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+6*(54+32-1)$
-301181599	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-301327557	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-6*(54+32-1)$
-301181617	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5*4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-301327641	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-6*(5^*4*(3+2)-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-301327971	$9^8 * -7 - (6 - 5 + 43) * 21$	-301525746	$9^8 * -7 + (6 - 5^4) * 321$
-301328211	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (5 * 43 - 21)$	-301529598	$9^8 * -7 - (6 + 5^4) * 321$
-301328384	$9^8 * -7 - (65 - 4/3) * 21$	-301951071	$9^8 * -7 - 6^5/4 * 321$
-301328440	$9^8 * -7 - (65 + 4/3) * 21$	-301989105	$-9 * ((8^{\wedge}(7+6-5) - 43) * 2 - 1)$
-301328463	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (5 * 43 + 21)$	-301989123	$-9 * ((8^{\wedge}(7+6-5) - 43) * 2 + 1)$
-301328535	$9^8 * -7 + (6 - 54) * (32 - 1)$	-301990653	$-9 * ((8^{\wedge}(7+6-5) + 43) * 2 - 1)$
-301328580	$9^8 * -7 - (6 * 5 + 43) * 21$	-301990671	$-9 * ((8^{\wedge}(7+6-5) + 43) * 2 + 1)$
-301328652	$9^8 * -7 - (6 - 5 + 4) * 321$	-302071263	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4) * 321$
-301328703	$9^8 * -7 - (65 + 4) * (3 + 21)$	-302071281	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4) * 321$
-301328802	$9^8 * -7 + 65 * (4 - 32 + 1)$	-302099511	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 321$
-301328853	$9^8 * -7 + 6 * (5 * 4 - 321)$	-302099529	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 321$
-301328871	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (5^4 - 321)$	-302108499	$9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) - 4) * 321$
-301329060	$9^8 * -7 - (65 - 4) * (32 + 1)$	-302108517	$-9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) - 4) * 321$
-301329186	$9^8 * -7 - (65 + 4) * (32 - 1)$	-302111067	$9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) + 4) * 321$
-301329294	$9^8 * -7 - (6 + 5 - 4) * 321$	-302111085	$-9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) + 4) * 321$
-301329324	$9^8 * -7 - (65 + 4) * (32 + 1)$	-302116203	$9 - (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4) * 321$
-301329336	$9^8 * -7 - 654 * (3 + 2^{\wedge} - 1)$	-302116221	$-9 - (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 - 5 * 4) * 321$
-301329603	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (5 - 432 + 1)$	-302119413	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 - 4) * 321$
-301329615	$9^8 * -7 + 6 * (5 - 432 - 1)$	-302119431	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5/4) * 321$
-301329663	$9^8 * -7 - 654 * (3 + 2 - 1)$	-302120055	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * 321$
-301329675	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (5 + 432 + 1)$	-302120073	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5 + 4) * 321$
-301329756	$9^8 * -7 - (65 + 4^{\wedge}3) * 21$	-302125191	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * 321$
-301329777	$9^8 * -7 - 65 * (43 - 2 + 1)$	-302125209	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 - 4) * 321$
-301329907	$9^8 * -7 - 65 * (43 + 2 - 1)$	-302125833	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5/4) * 321$
-301330037	$9^8 * -7 - 65 * (43 + 2 + 1)$	-302125851	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5/4) * 321$
-301330299	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (543 - 2 + 1)$	-302129043	$9 - (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) * 321$
-301330311	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (543 + 2 - 1)$	-302134179	$9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) - 4) * 321$
-301330622	$9^8 * -7 - (6 + 5) * (4 + 321)$	-302134197	$-9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) - 4) * 321$
-301330882	$9^8 * -7 + 65 * (4 - 3 * 21)$	-302136747	$9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) + 4) * 321$
-301331397	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * 5 * ((4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-302136765	$-9 - (8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5) + 4) * 321$
-301331727	$9^8 * -7 + 65 * 4 * (3 - 21)$	-302145735	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * 321$
-301331788	$9^8 * -7 - (6 + 5) * (432 - 1)$	-302145753	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 + 4) * 321$
-301331810	$9^8 * -7 - (6 + 5) * (432 + 1)$	-302173983	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) * 321$
-301331862	$9^8 * -7 - (6 + 5 + 4) * 321$	-302174001	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5 * 4) * 321$
-301332279	$9^8 * -7 - 654 * (3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-302271705	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (54^{\wedge}3 - 21)$
-301332444	$9^8 * -7 - (65 * 4 - 3) * 21$	-302271957	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (54^{\wedge}3 + 21)$
-301332570	$9^8 * -7 - (65 * 4 + 3) * 21$	-302508027	$9^8 * (((-7 - 6) / (5 + 4))^{\wedge}3 * 2 - 1)$
-301332572	$9^8 * -7 - 65 * (4^{\wedge}3 + 21)$	-303096135	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (543^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-301332702	$9^8 * -7 - 65 * (43 * 2 + 1)$	-303096147	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (543^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-301332723	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (5^4 + 321)$	-303299113	$9 - 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * (5/4 + 321)$
-301333287	$9^8 * -7 - 65 * 4 * (3 + 21)$	-303299131	$-9 - 8 * 7^{\wedge}6 * (5/4 + 321)$
-301333788	$9^8 * -7 - (6 * 54 - 3) * 21$	-303317055	$-9 / (8 * 7 / (6 / (5^{\wedge}4 - 3)))^{\wedge}2 - 2 + 1$
-301333914	$9^8 * -7 - (6 * 54 + 3) * 21$	-303317057	$-9 / (8 * 7 / (6 / (5^{\wedge}4 - 3)))^{\wedge}2 - 2 - 1$
-301334545	$9^8 * -7 + (6 - 54^{\wedge}3) / 21$	-303727623	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 321$
-301334721	$9^8 * -7 + 6 * (5 - 4 * 321)$	-303727641	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 + 5^{\wedge}4) * 321$
-301336557	$9^8 * -7 + 6 * 5 * (4 - 321)$	-303792039	$9^8 * -7 + 6 * 5 * (4 - 321)$
-301336797	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * 5 * (4 + 321)$	-303854247	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * 5 * (4 + 321)$
-301336821	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * 543 * (2 + 1)$	-303887295	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * ((5 + 4) * 32 - 1))$
-301336980	$9^8 * -7 - (6 + 5) * 43 * 21$	-303887439	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * ((5 + 4) * 32 - 1))$
-301337409	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (54 * 32 - 1)$	-303904911	$9 - 87 * ((6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-301337421	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (54 * 32 + 1)$	-303904929	$-9 - 87 * ((6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-301337961	$9^8 * -7 - (6 * 5 + 4) * 321$	-303905085	$9 - 87 * ((6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-301339977	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * 5 * (432 - 1)$	-303905103	$-9 - 87 * ((6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-301340001	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (5 * 432 - 1)$	-304633665	$9^8 * -7 + (6 - 54^{\wedge}3) * 21$
-301340013	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (5 * 432 + 1)$	-304633917	$9^8 * -7 - (6 + 54^{\wedge}3) * 21$
-301340037	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * 5 * (432 + 1)$	-304678503	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * 5 * (432 - 1)$
-301341171	$9^8 * -7 - (6 + 5) * 4 * 321$	-304694055	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * 5 * (432 + 1)$
-301341447	$9^8 * -7 - (6 * 5 * 4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1)$	-304943895	$9 * ((8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4)) * 32 + 1)$
-301342356	$9^8 * -7 - (6/54)^{\wedge} - 3 * 21$	-304943913	$9 * ((8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4)) * 32 - 1)$
-301344381	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * (5 + 4) * 321$	-304946127	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) * 32 + 1)$
-301348641	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * ((5 * 4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-304946271	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) * 32 - 1)$
-301348653	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * ((5 * 4 * 3)^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-304946289	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4) * 32 + 1)$
-301386075	$9^8 * (-7 - (6/54)^{\wedge}3) + 21$	-304948503	$-9 * ((8 + 7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 4)) * 32 - 1)$
-301386117	$9^8 * (-7 - (6/54)^{\wedge}3) - 21$	-305534355	$-98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 43/2) - 1)$
-301414407	$9^8 * -7 - 65 * 4^{\wedge}3 * 21$	-305534551	$-98 * (7^{\wedge}6 * (5 + 43/2) + 1)$
-301423041	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 * 2 - 1)$	-305854668	$9 * (87 * (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * (3/2))) + 1$
-301423053	$9^8 * -7 - 6 * ((5 * 4)^{\wedge}3 * 2 + 1)$	-305854686	$9 * (87 * (6 - 5^{\wedge}4 * (3/2))) - 1$
-301447167	$9^8 * -7 - 65 * (43^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-305864064	$-9 * (87 * (6 + 5^{\wedge}4 * (3/2))) - 1$
-301447297	$9^8 * -7 - 65 * (43^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-305874391	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 + 321)$
-301489440	$9^8 * -7 - (6^{\wedge}5 - 43) * 21$	-305874409	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 + 321)$
-301491246	$9^8 * -7 - (6^{\wedge}5 + 43) * 21$	-305885766	$9 - (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 + 321)$
-301521447	$9^8 * -7 - 6^{\wedge}5 * (4 * 3 * 2 + 1)$	-305885784	$-9 - (8 * 7^{\wedge}6 - 5) * (4 + 321)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-305886815	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$	-338824323	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*4^{\wedge}3+21)$
-305887985	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4^{\wedge}3+2-1)$	-338824493	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)/4^{\wedge}-3+2)+1$
-305889016	$9-(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+321)$	-338824495	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)/4^{\wedge}-3+2)-1$
-305889034	$-9-(8*7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+321)$	-338824529	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)/4^{\wedge}-3+2)+1$
-305900391	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+321)$	-338824531	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)/4^{\wedge}-3+2)-1$
-305900409	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+321)$	-338824701	$9*((8-7^{\wedge}6*5)*4^{\wedge}3-21)$
-306511047	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-(6*5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3*(2+1)$	-338828859	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*4^{\wedge}3+21)$
-307819911	$9-87*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-338829003	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*4^{\wedge}3-21)$
-307819929	$-9-87*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-338829237	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*4^{\wedge}3-21)$
-307820085	$9-87*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-338829381	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*4^{\wedge}3+21)$
-307820103	$-9-87*((6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-338833539	$-9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*4^{\wedge}3-21)$
-311298960	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)*3-2-1)$	-338833709	$9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
-311299009	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6*54-3)/2-1)$	-338833745	$-9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*4^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
-311299205	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6*54-3)/2+1)$	-338833747	$-9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*4^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
-311299499	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6*54+3)/2+1)$	-338833917	$-9*((8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*4^{\wedge}3+21)$
-311424426	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-(6/5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}-2+1)$	-339770214	$-98*((7+6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-311687279	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-(654/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-339770410	$-98*((7+6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-314475705	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)*(32+1))$	-339830109	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*321)$
-314475849	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)*(32+1))$	-339830253	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*321)$
-316593387	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-21))$	-339861888	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*321)$
-316593531	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4^{\wedge}3-21))$	-339862032	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)*321)$
-317439991	$9-(8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}-4*(32-1)$	-339885000	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*321)$
-317440009	$-9-(8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}-4*(32-1)$	-339885144	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)*321)$
-318504717	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-339885384	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))*321$
-318505203	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-339885402	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))*321$
-318711069	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-321))$	-339890520	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))*321$
-318711213	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*(5*4-321))$	-339890538	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4))*321$
-320005263	$(9+8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5/(4^{\wedge}-3*-2)+1)$	-339890778	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*321)$
-320790384	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*543)*(-2-1)$	-339890922	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)*321)$
-321698952	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+6^{\wedge}8-5*4^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$	-339913890	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*321)$
-321887511	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)+2)+1)$	-339914034	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)*321)$
-321887529	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)+2)-1)$	-339945669	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)*321)$
-321887628	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-339945813	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5*4)*321)$
-321887700	$9*8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-340123161	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4*3)/2+1)$
-321887799	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)-2)+1)$	-340123357	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4*3)/2-1)$
-321887817	$9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-43)-2)-1)$	-340594632	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+(6/(5+4))^{\wedge}(3*2)-1)$
-322560000	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(7/-6)/5)^{\wedge}-4*(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-341693514	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*321)$
-322815038	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-32)+1)$	-341693658	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)*321)$
-322815234	$98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-32)-1)$	-342186615	$9-876*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-322820883	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)/2-1)$	-342186633	$-9-876*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-322842478	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-32)+1)$	-342187490	$9-876*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1$
-322842674	$98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-32)-1)$	-342187492	$9-876*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1$
-322879932	$9^{\wedge}8*((7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}-3)/-2-1)$	-342187508	$-9-876*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1$
-328593559	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)/2-1)$	-342187510	$-9-876*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1$
-328593755	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)/2+1)$	-342188367	$9-876*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-328784049	$-9*87*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-342188385	$-9-876*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-328785615	$-9*87*((6^{\wedge}5/4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-342328994	$98*(7-(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-329269024	$-98*((7*6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-342329190	$98*(7-(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-329269220	$-98*((7*6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-342330366	$-98*(7+(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-329299478	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)+1$	-342330562	$-98*(7+(6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-329299480	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)-1$	-343146479	$(-9-8)*(7*(6+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-329299622	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)+1$	-343254024	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+(6/(5+4))^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-329299624	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2)-1$	-344108628	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4+321)$
-332476001	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2)+1$	-344108772	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4+321))$
-332476003	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2)-1$	-344137878	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4+321)$
-332476145	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2)+1$	-344138022	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4+321))$
-332476147	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2)-1$	-344163750	$-98*((7-6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-333964988	$98*((7+6)*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-344163946	$-98*((7-6-5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-333965184	$98*((7+6)*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-344370121	$((9^{\wedge}8-7*65)*-4+3)*2+1$
-335638260	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-321))$	-344370123	$((9^{\wedge}8-7*65)*-4+3)*2-1$
-335638404	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4-321))$	-344370133	$((9^{\wedge}8-7*65)*-4-3)*2+1$
-335666790	$9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-321))$	-344370135	$((9^{\wedge}8-7*65)*-4-3)*2-1$
-335666934	$9*(-8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*(4-321))$	-344370852	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+(6^{\wedge}5/4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-337919991	$9-(8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}-4*(32+1)$	-344372484	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-6+5)+4*321$
-337920009	$-9-(8^{\wedge}(-7/6)/5)^{\wedge}-4*(32+1)$	-344372865	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-6+5)+4*321$
-338082264	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*321)$	-344373169	$-9+8*(76-(5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-338082408	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*321)$	-344374367	$9-8*(76+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-338671008	$(9-876)*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1$	-344374671	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-6+5)-4*321$
-338671874	$(9-876)*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1$	-344375052	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-6+5)-4*321$
-338671876	$(9-876)*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1$	-344376684	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7+(6^{\wedge}-5*4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-338672742	$(9-876)*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1$	-344377401	$((9^{\wedge}8+7*65)*-4+3)*2+1$
-338705064	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7+6^{\wedge}8-5*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-344377403	$((9^{\wedge}8+7*65)*-4+3)*2-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-344377413	$((9^8+7*65)^*-4-3)^*2+1$	-368943442	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5/4)^*32+1)$
-344377415	$((9^8+7*65)^*-4-3)^*2-1$	-368944030	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^*32-1)$
-344898750	$-98*((7-6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-368944226	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^*32+1)$
-344898946	$-98*((7-6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-368950302	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^*32-1)$
-345001386	$9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)-5^{\wedge}(4^*3)^*(2+1)$	-368950498	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^*32+1)$
-345493512	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7+(6/(5+4))^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-368951086	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5/4)^*32-1)$
-345702240	$(-9-876)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	-368951282	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5/4)^*32+1)$
-345703124	$(-9-876)*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1$	-368962846	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$
-345703126	$(-9-876)*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1$	-368975390	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*32-1)$
-345704010	$(-9-876)*(5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	-368975586	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*32+1)$
-346738994	$98*(7-(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-369009886	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^*4)^*32-1)$
-346739190	$98*(7-(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-369010082	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^*4)^*32+1)$
-346740366	$-98*(7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-369622758	$(9-8^*7)^*6*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-346740562	$-98*(7+(6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-369622993	$(9-8^*7)^*(6^*5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-347822500	$(-9/(8+7*(6-(5^*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$	-369623087	$(9-8^*7)^*(6^*5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-347983047	$9^{\wedge}8^*-7-(6^*5^*4^*3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-369623322	$(9-8^*7)^*6*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-348241031	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6/5*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$	-370354642	$98*(7-(6^{\wedge}5/4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1))$
-348241049	$(-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6/5*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$	-370356014	$-98*(7+(6^{\wedge}5/4)^{\wedge}(3-2+1))$
-348867684	$(-9/(8-7*(6+(5^*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$	-370907166	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*32-1)$
-349325214	$-98*((7+6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-370907362	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*32+1)$
-349325410	$-98*((7+6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-372795906	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*5^*43)^*21$
-349839981	$(9^*87-(6^{\wedge}5/4)^{\wedge}3)/21$	-375073664	$(9/8/-7*(6^{\wedge}5-4^*3)^{\wedge}-2)^{\wedge}-1$
-350042472	$9^{\wedge}8*(7-6^{\wedge}5-5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-377396096	$(9/8/-7*(6^{\wedge}5+4^*3)^{\wedge}-2)^{\wedge}-1$
-352321275	$9-(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)-4^*3)^*21$	-377650401	$(9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5/4)^*321$
-352321499	$9-(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)-4/3)^*21$	-377653281	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5/4^*321$
-352321509	$(9-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)*(4+3))^*(2+1)$	-377656179	$(-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5/4)^*321$
-352321555	$9-(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)+4/3)^*21$	-379774300	$(9/(8+7*(6-(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3^*2)))^{\wedge}-1$
-352321563	$(9+8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)*(4+3))^*(-2-1)$	-380476768	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4+32)-1)$
-352321573	$-9-(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)+4/3)^*21$	-381166551	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)*(43+2)-1)$
-352321779	$9-(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)+4^*3)^*21$	-381166632	$-9^*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43+2)+1)$
-355770387	$(9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*54/3)^*21$	-381184776	$-9*((8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(43+2)-1)$
-355770765	$(-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*54/3)^*21$	-386109764	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-357417564	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4-32)+1)$	-386109774	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)+5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-357417760	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4-32)-1)$	-387414239	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)+5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-358611624	$-9*(87+65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-387415489	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)+5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-358614360	$-9*(87+65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-387417989	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)+5^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1)$
-360005923	$(-9-8)*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-387418605	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)+(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*(2+1)$
-360139024	$-98*((7*6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-387418623	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)+(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*(2+1)$
-360139220	$-98*((7*6+5^{\wedge}4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-387422355	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)-(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*(2+1)$
-361064709	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+321))$	-387422373	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)-(5^{\wedge}4+3)^*(2+1)$
-361064853	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+321))$	-387422989	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)-5^{\wedge}4*(3+2-1)$
-363181958	$9*(8^*7-(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-387425489	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)-5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-363181960	$9*(8^*7-(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-387426739	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)-5^{\wedge}4*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-363182597	$-9*(8+7+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$	-388731204	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-363182599	$-9*(8+7+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-388731214	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6)-5*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-363182968	$-9*(8^*7+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$	-389191940	$9*((-8-7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
-363183237	$-9*(87+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-389191942	$9*((-8-7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
-363183255	$-9*(87+(6+5-4)^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-389191976	$-9*((8+7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^{\wedge}3+2)+1$
-364224312	$-9^*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43-21)$	-389191978	$-9*((8+7^{\wedge}(-6+5+4))^{\wedge}3+2)-1$
-364225635	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43-21)$	-391637970	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6/5)^*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$
-364225797	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43-2-1)$	-391771098	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6/5*(43^{\wedge}2+1))$
-364225860	$-9^*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-391771242	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5*(43^{\wedge}2+1))$
-364225959	$-9*(8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43+2)-1)$	-391904370	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6/5)^*(43^{\wedge}2+1)$
-364226013	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43+21)$	-394569135	$9^{\wedge}8*-7-654^{\wedge}3/(2+1)$
-364226040	$-9^*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43+2+1)$	-397517868	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-(6/5/4^*3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-364227336	$-9^*8*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43+21)$	-397771171	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)/2-1)$
-364239180	$-9*((8^*7^{\wedge}6-5)^*43-21)$	-397771367	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)/2+1)$
-364243050	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43-21)$	-398019380	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^*2-1)$
-364243428	$-9*(8^*7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43+21)$	-398254678	$9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^*2+1)$
-364255272	$-9^*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43-21)$	-399504366	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7-6)+543^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-364256595	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43-21)$	-400240386	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54/3)^*21$
-364256973	$-9*(8*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43+21)$	-400241205	$(9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*54)^*3)^*21$
-364258296	$-9^*8*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*43+21)$	-400241385	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*54)^*3^*21$
-366987166	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*32-1)$	-400241403	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*54)^*3^*21$
-366987362	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)^*32+1)$	-400241583	$(-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*54)^*3)^*21$
-368884446	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^*4)^*32-1)$	-400242213	$(9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*3)^*21$
-368884642	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5^*4)^*32+1)$	-400242393	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*3^*21$
-368918942	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*32-1)$	-400242411	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*3^*21$
-368919138	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*32+1)$	-400242591	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*3)^*-21$
-368931486	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	-400243410	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54/3)^*21$
-368931682	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3/2+1)$	-401888967	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-432)+1)$
-368943246	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5/4)^*32-1)$	-401888983	$9+8*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-432)-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-401888985	$-9+8*(7^6*(5-432)+1)$	-430467543	$((9^8+7^6)^*-5+43)^*2+1$
-401889001	$-9+8*(7^6*(5-432)-1)$	-430467545	$((9^8+7^6)^*-5+43)^*2-1$
-402653079	$9-(8^7+6-5-4)^*(3+21)$	-430467715	$((9^8+7^6)^*-5-43)^*2+1$
-402653097	$-9-(8^7+6-5-4)^*(3+21)$	-430467717	$((9^8+7^6)^*-5-43)^*2-1$
-402653271	$9-(8^7+6-5+4)^*(3+21)$	-432155317	$((-9-8)/(7+(6^5/4)^3-2))^{\wedge-1}$
-403367928	$9*(8-7^6*(5^4)^3/21)$	-435147835	$(9-8^7/6)^*((5^4-3)^*2+1)$
-403368072	$-9*(8+7^6*(5^4)^3/21)$	-435170245	$(-9-8^7/6)^*((5^4-3)^*2+1)$
-403535776	$-98*(7^6*5*(4+3)-2-1)$	-435250158	$9^8*(-7-6/54-3)+21$
-403536021	$-98*(7^6*5*(4+3)-2^{\wedge-1})$	-435250200	$9^8*(-7-6/54-3)-21$
-405636503	$9-8*(7^6-5)^*(432-1)$	-437682287	$(98-7^6*5^{\wedge}(4+3))/21$
-405636521	$-9-8*(7^6-5)^*(432-1)$	-438040953	$(9-8*7^6*5)^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-405651588	$9-(8*7^6-5)^*(432-1)$	-438044295	$(9-8*7^6*5)^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-405655898	$9-(8*7^6+5)^*(432-1)$	-438124827	$98*(7^6*(5-43)+2^{\wedge-1})$
-405655916	$-9-(8*7^6+5)^*(432-1)$	-438124925	$98*(7^6*(5-43)-2^{\wedge-1})$
-405670983	$9-8*(7^6+5)^*(432-1)$	-438137689	$9^8+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^2)+1)$
-405671001	$-9-8*(7^6+5)^*(432-1)$	-438372987	$9^8+7^6*(5-4^{\wedge}(3^2)-1)$
-406577647	$9-8*((7^6-5)^*432-1)$	-438705459	$9^8-(7^6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^2)-1)$
-406577663	$9-8*((7^6-5)^*432+1)$	-438746409	$9^8-(7^6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^2)-1)$
-406577665	$-9-8*((7^6-5)^*432-1)$	-438940747	$9^8-(7^6-5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^2)+1)$
-406577681	$-9-8*((7^6-5)^*432+1)$	-438981717	$9^8-(7^6+5)^*(4^{\wedge}(3^2)+1)$
-406594980	$-9*8*(7^6*(5+43)+2^{\wedge-1})$	-439314179	$9^8-7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^2)-1)$
-406595079	$-9*(8*(7^6*(5+43)+2)-1)$	-439342031	$(9-8^7/6)^*((5^4+3)^*2+1)$
-406612207	$9-8*((7^6+5)^*432-1)$	-439364657	$(-9-8^7/6)^*((5^4+3)^*2+1)$
-406612223	$9-8*((7^6+5)^*432+1)$	-439549477	$9^8-7^6*(5+4^{\wedge}(3^2)+1)$
-406612225	$-9-8*((7^6+5)^*432-1)$	-441066003	$98-7^6*(5^4*3^2-1)$
-406612241	$-9-8*((7^6+5)^*432+1)$	-441066199	$-98-7^6*(5^4*3^2-1)$
-407518807	$9-8*(7^6-5)^*(432+1)$	-441301301	$98-7^6*(5^4*3^2+1)$
-407518825	$-9-8*(7^6-5)^*(432+1)$	-441301497	$-98-7^6*(5^4*3^2+1)$
-407533962	$9-(8*7^6-5)^*(432+1)$	-442759527	$(9+8*7^6*5)^*(-4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-407533980	$-9-(8*7^6-5)^*(432+1)$	-442762905	$(9+8*7^6*5)^*(-4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-407538292	$9-(8*7^6+5)^*(432+1)$	-443221794	$-9^8*(7+(6/(5+4))^3+2+1)$
-407538310	$-9-(8*7^6+5)^*(432+1)$	-444713211	$-9*(8*7^6*(54-3/2)-1)$
-407553447	$9-8*(7^6+5)^*(432+1)$	-444713292	$-9*8*(7^6*(54-3/2)+1)$
-407553465	$-9-8*(7^6+5)^*(432+1)$	-450007353	$9*(8-7^6*5*(4^3+21))$
-408020711	$(9^8+7^6/5^{\wedge}4)^*(-3-2^{\wedge}1)$	-450007497	$-9*(8+7^6*5*(4^3+21))$
-411278111	$9*((8-7^6)^{\wedge}5-4^3\wedge 2)+1$	-451066194	$9*(8+7^6*(5-432+1))$
-411300887	$9-8*(7^6*(5+432)-1)$	-451066338	$9*(-8+7^6*(5-432+1))$
-411300903	$9-8*(7^6*(5+432)+1)$	-452125026	$9*(8+7^6*(5-432)+1)$
-411300905	$-9-8*(7^6*(5+432)-1)$	-452125044	$9*(8+7^6*(5-432)-1)$
-411300921	$-9-8*(7^6*(5+432)+1)$	-452125170	$9*(-8+7^6*(5-432)+1)$
-413350236	$-9*876/5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-452125188	$9*(-8+7^6*(5-432)-1)$
-415047934	$-98*((7^6-5)^*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-452198055	$(-9-8*7^6)^*(5^4*3^2-1)$
-415048130	$-98*((7^6-5)^*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-452198745	$(-9-8*7^6)^*(5^4*3^2+1)$
-415083214	$-98*((7^6+5)^*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-452984535	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)-4)^*3-21$
-415083410	$-98*((7^6+5)^*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-452985129	$-9*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)+4)^*3+21$
-415686142	$(9+8)*(-7/(6-5^4*3)^{\wedge-2}+1)$	-453183876	$9*(8+7^6*(5-432-1))$
-415686176	$(-9-8)*(7/(6-5^4*3)^{\wedge-2}+1)$	-453184020	$9*(-8+7^6*(5-432-1))$
-417712626	$9^8*(7+6/(5+4))^3-2-1)$	-456209208	$-9*8*7^6*(54-3/21)$
-421041142	$(9+8)*(-7/(6+5^4*3)^{\wedge-2}+1)$	-456341004	$9*(8-(7^6-5)^*(432-1))$
-421041176	$(-9-8)*(7*(6+5^4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-456341148	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)^*(432-1))$
-421721001	$-9/(8/(7*(65^4*3-2)+1))$	-456379794	$9*(8-(7^6+5)^*(432-1))$
-422495595	$9^8*((-76/54-3)^*2-1)$	-456379938	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)^*(432-1))$
-423418679	$9*8-7^6*((5^4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-456478111	$9-8*7^6*(54*3^2-1)$
-423653977	$9*8-7^6*((5^4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-456478129	$-9-8*7^6*(54*3^2-1)$
-423698727	$9*(8-7/((6^5+4)/3)^{\wedge-2}+1)$	-457399791	$9*(8-(7^6-5)^*432+1)$
-423698729	$9*(8-7/((6^5+4)/3)^{\wedge-2}-1)$	-457399809	$9*(8-(7^6-5)^*432-1)$
-423698871	$-9*(8+7/((6^5+4)/3)^{\wedge-2}+1)$	-457399933	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)^*432-1)$
-423698873	$-9*(8+7/((6^5+4)/3)^{\wedge-2}-1)$	-457399953	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)^*432+1)$
-425684220	$9^8*(-7+6/54-3)+21$	-457416999	$-9*(8*(7^6*54-32)-1)$
-425684262	$9^8*(-7+6/54-3)-21$	-457417017	$-9*(8*(7^6*54-32)+1)$
-427431630	$9^8-7^6*((5^4)^3/2-1)$	-457418655	$9*(8*(7^6*54+3^2)+1)$
-427666928	$9^8-7^6*((5^4)^3/2+1)$	-457418673	$9*(8*(7^6*54+3^2)-1)$
-428605113	$(9-8*7^6)^*(5^4*3^2-1)$	-457418907	$-9*(8*(7^6*54-3)-21)$
-428605767	$(9-8*7^6)^*(5^4*3^2+1)$	-457419015	$-9*(8*7^6*54-32-1)$
-430006738	$(-9-8)*(7^6*5^4*3-21)$	-457419033	$-9*(8*7^6*54-32+1)$
-430007452	$(-9-8)*(7^6*5^4*3+21)$	-457419195	$-9*(8*(7^6*54+3/2)-1)$
-430466703	$((9^8-7^6)^*-5+43)^*2+1$	-457419222	$9*(-8*7^6*54+3^2+1)$
-430466705	$((9^8-7^6)^*-5+43)^*2-1$	-457419248	$-9*8*(7^6*54+3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-430466875	$((9^8-7^6)^*-5-43)^*2+1$	-457419376	$9*8*(7^6*54+3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-430466877	$((9^8-7^6)^*-5-43)^*2-1$	-457419402	$-9*(8*7^6*54+3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-430466889	$9^8*(-7+6-5-4)+321$	-457419474	$-9*(8*7^6*54-3+21)$
-430467531	$9^8*(-7+6-5-4)-321$	-457419501	$-9*(8*(7^6*54+3)-2-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-457419663	$-9*(8*(7^6*54+3+2))-1$	-482028340	$98-(7^6+5)*((4^3)^2+1)$
-457419717	$-9*(8*(7^6*54+3)+21)$	-482028366	$9*8-(7^6+5)*(4^3+2+1)$
-457419879	$-9*(8/7^6-6*54+3*21)$	-482028510	$9*-8-(7^6+5)*((4^3)^2+1)$
-457419951	$-9*(8*(7^6*54+3^2))-1$	-482360802	$98-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2-1)$
-457419969	$-9*(8*(7^6*54+3^2)+1)$	-482360828	$9*8-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2-1)$
-457421607	$-9*(8*(7^6*54+32))-1$	-482360972	$-9*8-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2-1)$
-457421625	$-9*(8*(7^6*54+32)+1)$	-482360998	$-98-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2-1)$
-457438671	$9*(8-(7^6+5)*432+1)$	-482596100	$98-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2+1)$
-457438689	$9*(8-(7^6+5)*432-1)$	-482596126	$9*8-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2+1)$
-457438815	$-9*(8*(7^6+5)*432-1)$	-482596270	$-9*8-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2+1)$
-457438833	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*432+1)$	-482596296	$-98-7^6*(5+(4^3)^2+1)$
-458360495	$9-8*7^6*(54*3^2+1)$	-482831532	$-9*8*(7^6*(54+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-458360513	$-9-8*7^6*(54*3^2+1)$	-482831631	$-9*(8*(7^6*(54+3)+2)-1)$
-458458596	$9*(8-(7^6-5)*(432+1))$	-488273367	$9*876-(5^4)^3*2-1$
-458458740	$-9*(8+(7^6-5)*(432+1))$	-488280364	$9+876-(5^4)^3*2+1$
-458497566	$9*(8-(7^6+5)*(432+1))$	-488280366	$9+876-(5^4)^3*2-1$
-458497710	$-9*(8+(7^6+5)*(432+1))$	-488282116	$9-876-(5^4)^3*2+1$
-458629416	$-9*8*7^6*(54+3/21)$	-488282118	$9-876-(5^4)^3*2-1$
-461183982	$-98*(7^6*5/4*32-1)$	-488282134	$-9-876-(5^4)^3*2+1$
-461184178	$-98*(7^6*5/4*32+1)$	-488282136	$-9-876-(5^4)^3*2-1$
-461654604	$9*(8-7^6*(5+432-1))$	-488289133	$-9*876-(5^4)^3*2+1$
-461654748	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+432-1))$	-488289135	$-9*876-(5^4)^3*2-1$
-462323232	$(-9/8/(7^6*543)^2)^{\wedge}-1$	-489457161	$9^8*(7/6*-5/(4/3)^{\wedge}-2-1)$
-462713436	$9*(8-7^6*(5+432)+1)$	-489987260	$-98*(7^6-5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-462713454	$9*(8-7^6*(5+432)-1)$	-490028910	$-98*(7^6+5)*(43-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-462713580	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+432))-1$	-492645786	$9^8*(7/6*(5+4)-3)+21$
-462713598	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+432)+1)$	-492645828	$9^8*(7/6*(5+4)-3)-21$
-463772286	$9*(8-7^6*(5+432+1))$	-495028494	$(9^8-765)*(-4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-463772430	$-9*(8+7^6*(5+432+1))$	-495046089	$(9^8+765)*(-4*3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-470478253	$98-7^6*((5^4)^3/2-1)$	-495452087	$9*(8-7^6*5*4^3+2)+1$
-470478279	$9*8-7^6*((5^4)^3/2-1)$	-495452089	$9*(8-7^6*5*4^3+2)-1$
-470478423	$9*-8-7^6*((5^4)^3/2-1)$	-495452231	$-9*(8+7^6*5*4^3+2)+1$
-470478449	$-98-7^6*((5^4)^3/2-1)$	-495452233	$-9*(8+7^6*5*4^3+2)-1$
-470713551	$98-7^6*((5^4)^3/2+1)$	-495751522	$-98*((7^6-5)*43-2-1)$
-470713577	$9*8-7^6*((5^4)^3/2+1)$	-495751718	$-98*((7^6-5)*43-2+1)$
-470713721	$9*-8-7^6*((5^4)^3/2+1)$	-495751767	$-98*((7^6-5)*43-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-470713747	$-98-7^6*((5^4)^3/2+1)$	-495751865	$-98*((7^6-5)*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-472693494	$-98*((7^6-5)*(43-2))-1$	-495751914	$-98*((7^6-5)*43+2-1)$
-472693690	$-98*((7^6-5)*(43-2)+1)$	-495752110	$-98*((7^6-5)*43+2+1)$
-472713584	$-98*(7^6*(5+4+32))-1$	-495793662	$-98*((7^6+5)*43-2-1)$
-472713780	$-98*(7^6*(5+4+32)+1)$	-495793858	$-98*((7^6+5)*43-2+1)$
-472733674	$-98*((7^6+5)*(43-2))-1$	-495793907	$-98*((7^6+5)*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-472733870	$-98*((7^6+5)*(43-2)+1)$	-495794005	$-98*((7^6+5)*43+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-473505516	$(9^8-765)*(-4*3+2-1)$	-495794054	$-98*((7^6+5)*43+2-1)$
-473511621	$(9^8-7^6*5)*(-4-3*2-1)$	-495794250	$-98*((7^6+5)*43+2+1)$
-473516241	$(9^8+7^6*5)*(-4-3*2-1)$	-497656152	$-98*((7+6)*5^4*(3/2)-1)$
-473522346	$(9^8+765)*(-4*3+2-1)$	-497656348	$-98*((7+6)*5^4*(3/2)+1)$
-474609132	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3+2)+1)$	-499771440	$9*8*(7^6*(5-4^3)+21)$
-474609618	$9^{\wedge}((8+7)/6)*(-5^{\wedge}(4+3+2)-1)$	-499772763	$9*(8*7^6*(5-4^3)+21)$
-476089488	$(9+8)*(7^6-6)^{\wedge}5/(4+(3/2)^{\wedge}-1)$	-499772933	$9*(8*7^6*(5-4^3)+2)+1$
-481184312	$98+7^6*(5-(4^3)^2+1)$	-499772935	$9*(8*7^6*(5-4^3)+2)-1$
-481184338	$9*8+7^6*(5-(4^3)^2+1)$	-499772969	$9*(8*7^6*(5-4^3)-2)+1$
-481184482	$-9*8+7^6*(5-(4^3)^2+1)$	-499772971	$9*(8*7^6*(5-4^3)-2)-1$
-481184508	$-98+7^6*(5-(4^3)^2+1)$	-499773141	$9*(8*7^6*(5-4^3)-21)$
-481419610	$98+7^6*(5-(4^3)^2-1)$	-499774464	$9*8*(7^6*(5-4^3)-21)$
-481419636	$9*8+7^6*(5-(4^3)^2-1)$	-501516372	$-98*(7^6-5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-481419780	$-9*8+7^6*(5-(4^3)^2-1)$	-501559002	$-98*(7^6+5)*(43+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-481419806	$-98+7^6*(5-(4^3)^2-1)$	-502211658	$(9^8*-7/6*5+43)*2+1$
-481752082	$98-(7^6-5)*((4^3)^2-1)$	-502211660	$(9^8*-7/6*5+43)*2-1$
-481752108	$9*8-(7^6-5)*(4^3+2)-1$	-502211830	$(9^8*-7/6*5-43)*2+1$
-481752252	$-9*8-(7^6-5)*((4^3)^2-1)$	-502211832	$(9^8*-7/6*5-43)*2-1$
-481752278	$-98-(7^6-5)*((4^3)^2-1)$	-503317623	$-9*((8^7/(6/5)+4)*32-1)$
-481793032	$98-(7^6+5)*((4^3)^2-1)$	-503739243	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7^6*54*3)*21$
-481793058	$9*8-(7^6+5)*(4^3+2)-1$	-505979938	$98-(7/(6-54^3))^{\wedge}-2^{\wedge}1$
-481793202	$9*-8-(7^6+5)*((4^3)^2-1)$	-505980019	$9+8-(7/(6-54^3))^{\wedge}-2^{\wedge}1$
-481793228	$-98-(7^6+5)*((4^3)^2-1)$	-505980053	$-9-8-(7/(6-54^3))^{\wedge}-2^{\wedge}1$
-481886199	$-9*(8^7*(6+5^4/32))-1$	-505980134	$-98-(7/(6-54^3))^{\wedge}-2^{\wedge}1$
-481886217	$-9*(8^7*(6+5^4/32)+1)$	-508243437	$(9-8*7^6*5^4)/3^{\wedge}(-2-1)$
-481987370	$98-(7^6-5)*((4^3)^2+1)$	-508243535	$9*8*(7^6*5^4*-3+2)+1$
-481987396	$9*8-(7^6-5)*(4^3+2)+1$	-508243537	$9*8*(7^6*5^4*-3+2)-1$
-481987540	$9*-8-(7^6-5)*((4^3)^2+1)$	-508243823	$9*8*(7^6*5^4*-3-2)+1$
-481987566	$-98-(7^6-5)*((4^3)^2+1)$	-508243825	$9*8*(7^6*5^4*-3-2)-1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-508243923	$(-9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^4) / 3^{(-2-1)}$	-558126855	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6*(5^4-32)+1)$
-508687047	$9^8 \cdot 7 - (6^5 \cdot 4)^{(3+2-1)}$	-558126857	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6*(5^4-32)-1)$
-510596651	$9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (543-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-558126873	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6*(5^4-32)+1)$
-510596669	$-9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (543-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-558727914	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-511067243	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 543-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-559068039	$9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-511067251	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 543+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-559068057	$-9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-511067261	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 543-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-559198510	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4 \cdot 4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-511067269	$-9 \cdot 8^*(7^6 \cdot 543+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-559406748	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4 \cdot 4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-511180735	$(9^*8-7)^*(6^*5^*-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-559433808	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4 \cdot 4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-511180865	$(9^*8-7)^*(6^*5^*-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-559600953	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-511537843	$9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (543+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-559602858	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-511537861	$-9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (543+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-559603971	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-513537813	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(54^*3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-559604484	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-513537957	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(54^*3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-559605208	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-514596069	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*54^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-559605218	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-514596087	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*54^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-559605591	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-514597365	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*54^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-559605699	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-514597383	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*54^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-559605744	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-515324708	$9 \cdot (8^*7+6)^{\wedge}5 / (4/3)^{\wedge}2+1$	-559605748	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-515655495	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(54^*3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-559605788	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-515655639	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(54^*3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-559606077	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-518809942	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43+2)-1)$	-559606176	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-518810138	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(43+2)+1)$	-559606302	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-518828464	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5-4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-559606365	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-518828660	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5-4)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-559606401	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-518831992	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(-54+3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-559606575	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-518835520	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4)^*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-559608171	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-518835716	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6^*5+4)^*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-559608345	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-518854042	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(43+2)-1)$	-559608381	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-518854238	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(43+2)+1)$	-559608444	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-523158480	$(-9+8/7^*6)^*((5^4)^{\wedge}3-2+1)$	-559608570	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-528949895	$9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-3^*21)$	-559608669	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-528949913	$-9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-3^*21)$	-559608958	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-530361594	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+43-2)-1)$	-559608998	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-530361790	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+43-2)+1)$	-559609002	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-531177822	$(9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*43)^*21$	-559609047	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-531178002	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*43^*21$	-559609155	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-531178020	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*43^*21$	-559609528	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-531178200	$(-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*43)^*21$	-559609538	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-531184878	$(9+8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*43)^*21$	-559610262	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-531185058	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*43)^*21$	-559610775	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-531185076	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*43)^*21$	-559611888	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-531185214	$(9-8-7^{\wedge}6^*5^*43)^*21$	-559613793	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-531185256	$(9-8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*43)^*-21$	-559807998	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-531185394	$9 \cdot (8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*43)^*21$	-559904404	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-531185412	$-9 \cdot (8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*43)^*21$	-561337047	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (6^5)^{\wedge}4^*321$
-531185592	$(9+8+7^{\wedge}6^*5^*43)^*-21$	-562087431	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (6^{\wedge}-5^*4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$
-531192270	$(9 \cdot (8+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*43)^*21$	-562914117	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32+1)$
-531192450	$9 \cdot (8+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*43^*21$	-565656383	$9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-3-21)$
-531192468	$-9 \cdot (8+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*43^*21$	-565656401	$-9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-3-21)$
-531192648	$(9+(8+7^{\wedge}6^*5)^*43)^*-21$	-566230535	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (7-6^*5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-536870840	$(9-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4)^*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-566230537	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (7-6^*5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-536870984	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4)^*(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-566231543	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (7-6^*5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-537851745	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 654^{\wedge}3 \cdot (2+1)$	-566231545	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (7-6^*5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-538074450	$(9^8-765)^*(-4^*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-568703562	$(9^8-(7+6)^{\wedge}5^*43)^*-21$
-538093575	$(9^8+765)^*(-4^*3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-570767634	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (7^*(6-5-4)^{\wedge}-3-2)+1)$
-542102040	$-9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3-21$	-571303535	$9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4+3-21)$
-542103363	$-9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-571303553	$-9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4+3-21)$
-542103741	$-9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-572832900	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(543-2)+1)$
-542105064	$-9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3+21$	-572832918	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(543-2)-1)$
-542123523	$-9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-572833044	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(543-2)-1)$
-542129283	$-9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-572833062	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(543-2)+1)$
-542129661	$-9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3+21)$	-573891750	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(543-2+1))$
-542149443	$-9^*(8^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3-21)$	-573891894	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(543-2+1))$
-542151144	$-9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3+21$	-574950564	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*543+2+1)$
-553420847	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+43)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-574950582	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*543+2-1)$
-553420945	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+43)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-574950600	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*543+2+1)$
-556300629	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (7-6)+54^{\wedge}3^*21$	-574950618	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*543-2-1)$
-557127315	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (7^*(6^{\wedge}-5/4^{\wedge}-3-2)+1)$	-574950708	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*543-2+1)$
-557185655	$9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32-1)$	-574950726	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*543-2-1)$
-557185673	$-9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4-32-1)$	-574950744	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*543+2-1)$
-558126839	$9 \cdot 8^*(7^6*(5^4-32)-1)$	-574950762	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*543+2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-576009432	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(543+2-1))$	-617421961	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32-1)$
-576009576	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2-1))$	-618363127	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32)-1)$
-577068264	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(543+2)+1)$	-618363143	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32)+1)$
-577068282	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(543+2)-1)$	-618363145	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32)-1)$
-577068408	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2)-1)$	-618363161	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32)+1)$
-577068426	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2)+1)$	-618394112	$(9/-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-578127114	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(543+2+1))$	-619304327	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32+1)$
-578127258	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(543+2+1))$	-619304345	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32+1)$
-582244901	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-620010213	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$
-584478720	$-9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-21)$	-620010247	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$
-584480043	$-9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-21)$	-621281201	$(9^*8+7)^*(6^*5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$
-584480213	$-9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-2)+1$	-621281359	$(9^*8+7)^*(6^*5*(4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$
-584480215	$-9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)-2)-1$	-622010246	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2-1)$
-584480249	$-9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+2)+1$	-622010280	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)/2+1)$
-584480251	$-9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+2)-1$	-622597528	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-584480421	$-9^*(8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+21)$	-622597724	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-584481744	$-9^*8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)+21)$	-622598165	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3-2^{\wedge}-1)$
-585421247	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-21)$	-622598263	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3/2-1)$
-585421265	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-21)$	-622598459	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54-3/2+1)$
-585421583	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+21)$	-622598557	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3/2-1)$
-585421601	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+21)$	-622598753	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3/2+1)$
-588009653	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-622598851	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*54+3+2^{\wedge}-1)$
-588009751	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-622599292	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3^{\wedge}2+1))$
-588379447	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3/21)$	-622599488	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-588379465	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3/21)$	-622638297	$9^{\wedge}8^*-7+65^{\wedge}4*(3-21)$
-590872478	$98^*((7-6^*5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-626833800	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32-1))$
-590872674	$98^*((7-6^*5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-626833944	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32-1))$
-591068399	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-21)$	-627892632	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32)+1)$
-591068417	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-21)$	-627892650	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32)-1)$
-591068735	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+21)$	-627892776	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32)-1)$
-591068753	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+21)$	-627892794	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32)+1)$
-593774503	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2-1)$	-628010345	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2-1)$
-595068570	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^*21))$	-628010379	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)/2+1)$
-595068714	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3^*21))$	-628363309	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2-1)$
-599539206	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+32)-1)$	-628951482	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32+1))$
-599539402	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4+32)+1)$	-628951626	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-32+1))$
-601774537	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-633983516	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4-321)$
-601774563	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-634037406	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4-321)$
-601774707	$9^*-8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-636010477	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$
-601774733	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-636010511	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}3-2)+1)$
-602245133	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-636363369	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3-21))$
-602245159	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-636363513	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3-21))$
-602245303	$9^*-8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-638599968	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}4)*321$
-602245329	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$	-639892813	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2)-1)$
-602480431	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-639893009	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2)+1)$
-602480457	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-639999990	$(-9-(8-7)^{\wedge}6)*(((5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-602480601	$-9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*(5/4^{\wedge}(-3-2)+1)$	-640000010	$(-9-(8-7)^{\wedge}6)*(((5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-602480627	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-640010509	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5/-4^{\wedge}-3+2+1)$
-602653513	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)/-6+5)^*4+3)^*21$	-640010543	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
-602654479	$((9^{\wedge}8-7)/-6-5)^*4-3)^*21$	-640010577	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*-4^{\wedge}3-2+1)$
-602951027	$98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-640010611	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*4^{\wedge}3+2+1)$
-602951053	$9^*8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-641901453	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5^*4)^*321$
-602951197	$9^*-8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-641961480	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5-4)^*-321$
-602951223	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$	-642005136	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5+4)^*-321$
-603976887	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4-321)$	-642016050	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5-4)^*-321$
-603979209	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4-3^*21)$	-642059706	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5+4)^*-321$
-603979560	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4-3-21)$	-642119733	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^*4)^*321$
-603979614	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4+3-21)$	-642512169	$9^{\wedge}8*((7+(6-5-4)^{\wedge}-3)^*-2-1)$
-603979938	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4-3+21)$	-642716415	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3-21))$
-603979992	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4+3+21)$	-642716559	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3-21))$
-603980343	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4+3^*21)$	-643220757	$9^{\wedge}8*(7^*(6^*(5+4)^{\wedge}-3-2)-1)$
-603982665	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4+3^*21)$	-644010609	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$
-605186447	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3+21)$	-644010643	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^*4^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$
-605186465	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3+21)$	-644992227	$9^{\wedge}8*((-7+6^{\wedge}-5^*4^{\wedge}3)^*2-1)$
-605304007	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2)-1)$	-645421218	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)^*321$
-605304203	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2)+1)$	-645689340	$(9^{\wedge}8-765)^*(-4^*3-2-1)$
-606634112	$(9/-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$	-645697665	$(-9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4^*3+2+1)$
-610833599	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+21)$	-645700152	$((9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6)^*-5+4)^*3+21$
-610833617	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+21)$	-645700218	$((9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6)^*-5-4)^*3-21$
-612220718	$-98^*7-6^*(5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}(3+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-645701412	$((9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6)^*-5+4)^*3+21$
-616833707	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3/2+1)$	-645701478	$((9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6)^*-5-4)^*3-21$
-617421943	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32-1)$	-645703965	$(-9^{\wedge}8-7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(4^*3+2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-645712290	$(9^8+765)^*(-4^3-2-1)$	-684193221	$9-87^6*5^*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-646409403	$9^8*((-7-6^{\wedge}5*4^3)^*2-1)$	-684195309	$9-87^6*(5^*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-647295138	$9^8*(7-65)/(4-3/21)$	-684195744	$9-87^6*(6^*5^*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-647540087	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^*21)$	-684195762	$-9-87^*(6^*5^*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-647540105	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3^*21)$	-684195918	$9-87^6*(6^*5^*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-648180873	$9^8*(-7*(6^{\wedge}5*4^3+2)-1)$	-684195936	$-9-87^*(6^*5^*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-648889461	$9^8*((-7+(6-5-4)^{\wedge}3)^*2-1)$	-684196353	$9-87^6*(5^*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-649983100	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4+321)$	-684198441	$9-87^6*5^*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-650038350	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4+321)$	-686011421	$(-9-8)^*(7+(6+5-4)^3\wedge 2-1)$
-651422513	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6*(54+3/2+1)$	-686011455	$(-9-8)^*(7+(6+5-4)^3\wedge 2+1)$
-654294576	$(9-8^{\wedge}7/6)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2-1)$	-686128870	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-654328272	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7/6)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2-1)$	-686129066	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(54/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-655359811	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6*5^{\wedge}4/3-21)$	-687153213	$9^8*((7-6-5)^*4+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-655360189	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6*5^{\wedge}4/3+21)$	-687187737	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+21))$
-656391674	$(9-8^{\wedge}7/6)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1)$	-687187881	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3+21))$
-656425478	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7/6)^*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1)$	-688746752	$9^*87-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-656861076	$9^8*(7*((6-5-4)^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$	-688746754	$9^*87-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-657187265	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-688746849	$98^*7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-657187363	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(54+3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-688746850	$98^*7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2\wedge 1$
-658598841	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+21)$	-688746851	$98^*7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-658598985	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-21)$	-688747430	$98+7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-658599011	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+2)+1$	-688747431	$98+7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2/1$
-658599013	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+2)-1$	-688747432	$98+7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-658599047	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-2)+1$	-688747439	$9+87-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-658599049	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-2)-1$	-688747441	$9+87-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-658599155	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-2)+1$	-688747444	$98-7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-658599157	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-2)-1$	-688747446	$98-7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-658599191	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+2)+1$	-688747459	$-9+87-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-658599193	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+2)-1$	-688747613	$9-87-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-658599219	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)-21)$	-688747626	$-98+7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-658599363	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)+21)$	-688747628	$-98+7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-660010873	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*(4^3+2)-1)$	-688747631	$-9-87-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-660010907	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6*5^*(4^3+2)-1)$	-688747633	$-9-87-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-660486150	$(9^8+7^{\wedge}6*54)^*(3-21)$	-688747640	$-98-7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-661657878	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-688747641	$-98-7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2/1$
-661658074	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-688747642	$-98-7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-661775130	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4-3^*21)$	-688748221	$-98^*7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-661776120	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6/5^{\wedge}4-3^*21)$	-688748222	$-98^*7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2\wedge 1$
-661893176	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-688748223	$-98^*7-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-661893372	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-688748318	$-9^*87-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2+1$
-661926816	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3/21))$	-688748320	$-9^*87-(6/54^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-661926960	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3/21))$	-689022207	$9^8+(7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4^3))^*(2+1)$
-664951887	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+21)$	-689728101	$9^8-(7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4^3))^*(2+1)$
-664952031	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-21)$	-690094071	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7*65/(4/3)^{\wedge}2-1)$
-664952057	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2)+1$	-690094089	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7*65/(4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-664952059	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2)-1$	-690341859	$9^8*((7-6-5)^*4-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-664952093	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-2)+1$	-694599624	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32-1))$
-664952095	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-2)-1$	-694599768	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32-1))$
-664952201	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-2)+1$	-695658456	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32)+1)$
-664952203	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-2)-1$	-695658474	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32)-1)$
-664952237	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2)+1$	-695658600	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32)-1)$
-664952239	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+2)-1$	-695658618	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32)+1)$
-664952265	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)-21)$	-696717300	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32+1))$
-664952409	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)+21)$	-696717450	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+32+1))$
-671088550	$(9-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-696954762	$(9^8-(76-5)^{\wedge}4*3)^*21$
-671088730	$(-9-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4)^*(3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-703305624	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3-2)+1)$
-672950993	$(9-8/7^{\wedge}6*5)^*((4^3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-703305820	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$
-672953567	$(-9-8/7^{\wedge}6*5)^*((4^3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-705295138	$(9/(8-(7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4)^3)^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-676331331	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)^*43-21)$	-714804846	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^3-2)-1)$
-676331709	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)^*43+21)$	-714805042	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*(4^3-2)+1)$
-677658311	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5/4^{\wedge}3-3^*2)+1$	-714865606	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^3-2)-1)$
-677658313	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5/4^{\wedge}3-3^*2)-1$	-714865802	$-98^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*(4^3-2)+1)$
-680244460	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+21)$	-715864149	$(9^8-(7+65)^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$
-680246224	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2+1)$	-717226641	$9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$
-680246469	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)+2^{\wedge}-1)$	-717226659	$-9+(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$
-680246567	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-2^{\wedge}-1)$	-717992091	$9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$
-680246812	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-2-1)$	-717992109	$-9-(8+7)^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)^*21$
-680248576	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4^{\wedge}3)-21)$	-719710380	$9^8*(-7-6)-543^{\wedge}(2+1)$
-680834691	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3+21))$	-722534399	$-9/(8/7*(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2+1$
-680834835	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3+21))$	-722534401	$-9/(8/7*(6^{\wedge}5+4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2-1$
-682362895	$(9-8/7^{\wedge}6*5)^*((4^3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-726099374	$(9^8-(76-5)^{\wedge}4/3)^*21$
-682365505	$(-9-8/7^{\wedge}6*5)^*((4^3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-727638906	$9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)-5^{\wedge}(4^3)^*(2+1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-729742047	$9^8 * -7 - 65^4 * (3+21)$	-774813618	$(9^8 - 76 * 5^4) * (3-21)$
-732068830	$98 + (7^6 - (5^4)^3) * (2+1)$	-774828342	$(9^8 - (7+6) * 5^4) * (3-21)$
-732069026	$-98 + (7^6 - (5^4)^3) * (2+1)$	-774828666	$(9^8 - 76 * (5+4)) * (3-21)$
-732362826	$9^8 (-8+7+6) - 5^4 (4^3) * (2+1)$	-774832284	$(9^8 - 7 * (65+4)) * (3-21)$
-732420990	$9+876 - (5^4)^3 * (2+1)$	-774833292	$(9^8 - 7 * (65-4)) * (3-21)$
-732422742	$9-876 - (5^4)^3 * (2+1)$	-774833418	$(9^8 - 7 * (6+5^4)) * (3-21)$
-732422760	$-9-876 - (5^4)^3 * (2+1)$	-774834930	$(9^8 + 7 * (6-5^4)) * (3-21)$
-732480924	$-9^8 (-8+7+6) - 5^4 (4^3) * (2+1)$	-774835146	$(9^8 - (76+5) * 4) * (3-21)$
-732539524	$(-9+8) * 7^6 - 5^4 (4^3) * (2+1)$	-774835794	$(9^8 - (7+65) * 4) * (3-21)$
-732774724	$98 - (7^6 + (5^4)^3) * (2+1)$	-774835866	$(9^8 - (76-5) * 4) * (3-21)$
-732774920	$-98 - (7^6 + (5^4)^3) * (2+1)$	-774836802	$(9^8 + (7-65) * 4) * (3-21)$
-735306330	$-9 * (8+7^6 * 5^4) * (3^4 - 2+1)$	-774839268	$(9^8 - 76 * 5/4) * (3-21)$
-737204844	$-9^8 (8-7+6) - 5^4 (4^3) * (2+1)$	-774839603	$((9^8 - 76) * (-5-4) + 3) * 2+1$
-737861110	$-98 * ((7^6 - 5) * 4^3 - 21)$	-774839605	$((9^8 - 76) * (-5-4) * 3) * 2-1$
-737862874	$-98 * ((7^6 - 5) * 4^3 - 2-1)$	-774839615	$((9^8 - 76) * (-5-4) - 3) * 2+1$
-737863070	$-98 * ((7^6 - 5) * 4^3 - 2+1)$	-774839617	$((9^8 - 76) * (-5-4) - 3) * 2-1$
-737863119	$-98 * ((7^6 - 5) * 4^3 - 2^4 - 1)$	-774839694	$9^8 * (-7-6-5) + 4 * 321$
-737863217	$-98 * ((7^6 - 5) * 4^3 + 2^4 - 1)$	-774839844	$(9^8 - 7/6 * 5^4) * (3-21)$
-737863266	$-98 * ((7^6 - 5) * 4^3 + 2-1)$	-774840075	$9^8 * (-7-6-5) + 4 * 3 * 21$
-737863462	$-98 * ((7^6 - 5) * 4^3 + 2+1)$	-774841881	$9^8 * (-7-6-5) - 4 * 3 * 21$
-737865226	$-98 * ((7^6 - 5) * 4^3 + 21)$	-774842112	$(9^8 + 7/6 * 5^4) * (3-21)$
-737923830	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4^3 - 21)$	-774842262	$9^8 * (-7-6-5) - 4 * 3 * 21$
-737925594	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4^3 - 2-1)$	-774842339	$((9^8 + 76) * (-5-4) + 3) * 2+1$
-737925790	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4^3 - 2+1)$	-774842341	$((9^8 + 76) * (-5-4) + 3) * 2-1$
-737925839	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4^3 - 2^4 - 1)$	-774842351	$((9^8 + 76) * (-5-4) - 3) * 2+1$
-737925937	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4^3 + 2^4 - 1)$	-774842353	$((9^8 + 76) * (-5-4) - 3) * 2-1$
-737925986	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4^3 + 2-1)$	-774842688	$(9^8 + 76 * 5/4) * (3-21)$
-737926182	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4^3 + 2+1)$	-774845154	$(9^8 - (7-65) * 4) * (3-21)$
-737927946	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * 4^3 + 21)$	-774846090	$(9^8 + (76-5) * 4) * (3-21)$
-749424032	$-98 * (7^6 * 5 * (4+3^2) - 1)$	-774846162	$(9^8 + (7+65) * 4) * (3-21)$
-749424228	$-98 * (7^6 * 5 * (4+3^2) + 1)$	-774846810	$(9^8 + (76+5) * 4) * (3-21)$
-751071207	$9+8 * 7^6 * (5-43) * 21$	-774847026	$(9^8 - 7 * (6-5^4)) * (3-21)$
-753317582	$((9^8 * -7+6) * 5+43) / 2-1$	-774848538	$(9^8 + 7 * (6+5^4)) * (3-21)$
-753317612	$((9^8 * -7-6) * 5+43) / 2-1$	-774848664	$(9^8 + 7 * (65-4)) * (3-21)$
-755293419	$(9+(8-7^6 * 5) * 4) * 321$	-774849672	$(9^8 + 7 * (65+4)) * (3-21)$
-755296299	$9+(8-7^6 * 5) * 4 * 321$	-774853290	$(9^8 + 76 * (5+4)) * (3-21)$
-755296317	$-9+(8-7^6 * 5) * 4 * 321$	-774853614	$(9^8 + (7+6) * 5^4) * (3-21)$
-755299197	$(-9+(8-7^6 * 5) * 4) * 321$	-774868338	$(9^8 + 76 * 5^4) * (3-21)$
-755301123	$(9+8-7^6 * 5^4) * 321$	-774873738	$(9^8 + 7 * 65^4) * (3-21)$
-755304003	$9+(8-7^6 * 5^4) * 321$	-774881802	$(9^8 + 7 * 6^5 * 4) * (3-21)$
-755304021	$-9+(8-7^6 * 5^4) * 321$	-774959076	$-9^8 * (7+(6+(5+4)^4) * 3) * 2-1$
-755306259	$(9-8-7^6 * 5^4) * 321$	-7749695978	$(9^8 + 76 * 5^4) * (3-21)$
-755306901	$(9-8+7^6 * 5^4) * -321$	-777599757	$9^8 ((8+7)/6) * ((-5^4)^{(3+2)+1})$
-755309139	$9-(8+7^6 * 5^4) * 321$	-777600243	$9^8 ((8+7)/6) * ((-5^4)^{(3+2)-1})$
-755309157	$-9-(8+7^6 * 5^4) * 321$	-777979062	$(9^8 - 7^6 * (54-3)) * -21$
-755312037	$(9+8+7^6 * 5^4) * -321$	-779026717	$(9^8 - (7+65^4)/3) * -21$
-755313963	$(9-(8+7^6 * 5) * 4) * 321$	-779026815	$(9^8 + (7-65^4)/3) * -21$
-755316843	$9-(8+7^6 * 5) * 4 * 321$	-780926975	$9 * (8^7 * -6+5) * 4^3 * 2+1$
-755316861	$-9-(8+7^6 * 5) * 4 * 321$	-780926977	$9 * (8^7 * -6+5) * 4^3 * 2-1$
-755319741	$(9+(8+7^6 * 5) * 4) * -321$	-785390949	$(9^8 - 7^6 * (5+43)) * -21$
-760921294	$-98 * ((7^6 - 5) * (4^3 + 2) - 1)$	-789071787	$(9^8 - (7+65)^4 * 3) * 21$
-760921490	$-98 * ((7^6 - 5) * (4^3 + 2) + 1)$	-790590519	$9+(8-7^6 * 5) * 4^3 * 21$
-760985974	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * (4^3 + 2) - 1)$	-790599222	$(98 - 7^6 * 5^4 * 4^3) * 21$
-760986170	$-98 * ((7^6 + 5) * (4^3 + 2) + 1)$	-790601103	$9+(8-7^6 * 5^4 * 4^3) * 21$
-763155288	$(9^8 - 7^6 * (54+3)) * -21$	-790601121	$-9+(8-7^6 * 5^4 * 4^3) * 21$
-765097893	$(9^8 - 7^6 * 5^4 * 3) * -21$	-790601182	$98 + 7^6 * -5 * 4^3 * 21$
-768868898	$(9/-8 * ((7^6 + 5)/4 - 3)^4)^{-1}$	-790601378	$-98 + 7^6 * -5 * 4^3 * 21$
-769182642	$(9/-8 * ((7^6 + 5)/4 + 3)^4)^{-1}$	-790601439	$9-(8+7^6 * 5^4 * 4^3) * 21$
-770701106	$-98 * (7+6 * 5 * (4^3 * 2 - 1))$	-790603338	$(98 + 7^6 * 5^4 * 4^3) * -21$
-770703458	$-98 * (7+6 * 5 * (5^4 * 3^2 - 1))$	-790612023	$9-(8+7^6 * 5) * 4^3 * 21$
-770703948	$-98 * (7+6 * 5^4 * 3^2 - 1)$	-790612041	$-9-(8+7^6 * 5) * 4^3 * 21$
-770704144	$-98 * (7+6 * 5^4 * 3^2 + 1)$	-792378531	$9^8 * (-76+5) / (4-3/21)$
-770704634	$-98 * (7+6 * 5^4 * 3^2 + 1)$	-795540480	$-98 * (7^6 * (5+4^3) - 21)$
-770706986	$-98 * (7+6 * 5^4 * 3^2 + 1)$	-795542244	$-98 * (7^6 * (5+4^3) - 2-1)$
-770799393	$(9-8 * 7^6 / 5) * ((4^3)^2 - 1)$	-795542440	$-98 * (7^6 * (5+4^3) - 2+1)$
-770873103	$(9-8 * 7^6 / 5) * ((4^3)^2 - 1)$	-795542489	$-98 * (7^6 * (5+4^3) - 2^4 - 1)$
-772483236	$-98 * (7^6 * (5+4^3 - 2) - 1)$	-795542587	$-98 * (7^6 * (5+4^3) + 2^4 - 1)$
-772483432	$-98 * (7^6 * (5+4^3 - 2) + 1)$	-795542636	$-98 * (7^6 * (5+4^3) + 2-1)$
-773985978	$(9^8 - 76 * 5^4) * (3-21)$	-795542832	$-98 * (7^6 * (5+4^3) + 2+1)$
-774722880	$-9^8 * (7+(6-(5+4)^4) * 2-1)$	-795544596	$-98 * (7^6 * (5+4^3) + 21)$
-774800154	$(9^8 - 7^6 * 5^4) * (3-21)$	-796914711	$9-8 * 7^6 * 5^4 * (4^3 * 2 - 1)$
-774808218	$(9^8 - 7^6 * 5^4) * (3-21)$	-796917143	$9-8 * 7^6 * (5^4 * 3^2 - 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-796917743	$9 \cdot 8^*(76 \cdot 5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-882467108	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 7^*65)^*(-43/2 + 1)$
-796917759	$9 \cdot 8^*(76 \cdot 5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-883727334	$9^{\wedge}8 * ((7^*6/54)^{\wedge}3 - 21)$
-796917761	$-9 \cdot 8^*(76 \cdot 5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$	-885976266	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (76 \cdot 5/4)^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$
-796917777	$-9 \cdot 8^*(76 \cdot 5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-887724117	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 7^*(6 - 54)^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$
-796918359	$9 \cdot 8^*76^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-889195806	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 54)^*(3 - 21)$
-796920791	$9 \cdot 8^*76^*5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$	-889418313	$-9^*(8/7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5^*43)^*21$
-797739579	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 5)^*43)^* - 21$	-889434567	$-9^*(8/7^{\wedge}6 \cdot 5^*43)^*21$
-797748609	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 5)^*43)^* - 21$	-889948223	$-9^*(8^*(7 - 6^*5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2 + 1$
-804519935	$9^*(8^*7^* - 6 - 5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1$	-889948225	$-9^*(8^*(7 - 6^*5^{\wedge}4/3))^{\wedge}2 - 1$
-804519937	$9^*(8^*7^* - 6 - 5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1$	-890367623	$9 \cdot 8^*7^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}4 + 321)$
-805133115	$9^{\wedge}8^*((7 - 6/54)/3 - 21)$	-890367641	$-9 \cdot 8^*7^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}4 + 321)$
-805197376	$(-9/(8^*7 - ((6+5)^*4)^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge} - 1$	-890397672	$9^{\wedge}8^* - 7 \cdot 65^{\wedge}4^*(32 + 1)$
-806727438	$9^{\wedge}8^*(7/6 - 5)^*(4 \cdot 3^{\wedge}2 - 21)$	-891213141	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76^*(5^*4)^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$
-810097239	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 7^{\wedge}6^*(5 - 43))^* - 21$	-896529132	$-9^*(8 + 76^*5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$
-811510407	$9^{\wedge}8^*(-7^*6 + 5^{\wedge}4/3^{\wedge}(2 + 1))$	-896531868	$-9^*(8 + 76^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1))$
-816293382	$(-9/(8^*7 + (6^{\wedge}5/4)^{\wedge}3 - 2))^{\wedge} - 1$	-896532543	$-9^*(8 + 76^*5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 - 1)$
-817873164	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 765)^*(-4^*(3 + 2) + 1)$	-896532561	$-9^*(8 + 76^*5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1)$
-817883709	$(-9^{\wedge}8 + 7^*6^*5)^*(4^*(3 + 2) - 1)$	-896533236	$-9^*(8 + 76^*(5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1))$
-817887378	$9^{\wedge}8^*(7 - 6^*5 + 4) + 321$	-896535972	$-9^*(8 + 76^*5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2 + 1))$
-817888020	$9^{\wedge}8^*(7 - 6^*5 + 4) - 321$	-896565852	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 54)^*3)^* - 21$
-817891689	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 7^*6^*5)^*(-4^*(3 + 2) + 1)$	-896572656	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54)^*3)^* - 21$
-817902234	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 765)^*(-4^*(3 + 2) + 1)$	-897792332	$9^{\wedge}8 - 7^{\wedge}6^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3 - 2 - 1)$
-818601644	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5 + 4^{\wedge}3 + 2) - 1)$	-898027630	$9^{\wedge}8 - 7^{\wedge}6^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3 - 2 + 1)$
-818601840	$-98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5 + 4^{\wedge}3 + 2) + 1)$	-898262928	$9^{\wedge}8 - 7^{\wedge}6^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3 + 2 - 1)$
-821960200	$9^{\wedge}8 - ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1)$	-898498226	$9^{\wedge}8 - 7^{\wedge}6^*((5^*4)^{\wedge}3 + 2 + 1)$
-823262328	$9^{\wedge}8^*7 + 65^{\wedge}4^* - 3^*21$	-898600447	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 7)^*(6/(5 + 43) - 21)$
-824765669	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (7 - 65)^{\wedge}4/3)^* - 21$	-898730154	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (7/6^*54)^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$
-827453637	$9^{\wedge}8^*(-7^*(6^*5 - 4)^*3^{\wedge}2 - 2 + 1)$	-899149706	$98^*(7^*(6 - 5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) + 1)$
-844953606	$9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6^*(5 - 43))^*21$	-899149902	$98^*(7^*(6 - 5^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2) - 1)$
-844955046	$9^*(8 + 7^{\wedge}6^*(5 - 43))^*21$	-900123273	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7/6^*54^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$
-844955190	$9^*(- 8 + 7^{\wedge}6^*(5 - 43))^*21$	-900988641	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76^*5^{\wedge}4^*3)^* - 21$
-844956630	$9^*(- 8 + 7^{\wedge}6^*(5 - 43))^*21$	-902817657	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76^*(5 + 4)^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$
-845190407	$9 + 8^*7^{\wedge}6^*(5 - 43^*21)$	-902831748	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*(6^{\wedge}5 + 43))^* - 21$
-845190425	$-9 + 8^*7^{\wedge}6^*(5 - 43^*21)$	-902844390	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*(6^{\wedge}5 - 43))^* - 21$
-849860067	$(9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5)^*43)^*21$	-902978853	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76^*(5^{\wedge}4 + 3))^* - 21$
-849860445	$(-9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5)^*43)^*21$	-902988429	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76^*(5^{\wedge}4 - 3))^* - 21$
-849932307	$(9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5)^*43)^*21$	-903157220	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (7^{\wedge}6 + 54)/3)^* - 21$
-849932685	$(-9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5)^*43)^*21$	-903157976	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (7^{\wedge}6 - 54)/3)^* - 21$
-854014074	$(9 + 8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5 - 432) + 1)$	-903369621	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*65^*4^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$
-854014108	$(9 + 8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5 - 432) - 1)$	-903470421	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76^*5^*4^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$
-854602327	$9 - 8^*7^{\wedge}6^*(5 + 43^*21)$	-903544293	$(9 - 8^*7^{\wedge}6^*5/4^{\wedge}3)^*(2 + 1)$
-854696422	$9 + 8^*7 - 65^{\wedge}4^*(32 - 1)$	-903544347	$(-9 - 8^*7^{\wedge}6^*5/4^{\wedge}3)^*(2 + 1)$
-854829045	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*6^{\wedge}5^*43)^* - 21$	-903648641	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76^*5^{\wedge}4/3)^* - 21$
-855690318	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*(65 + 4)^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$	-903871017	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76^*(5 + 4^{\wedge}3))^* - 21$
-859509819	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^{\wedge}6^*54/3)^* - 21$	-903872277	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (76 + 5)^*4^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$
-860816322	$-9^{\wedge}8^*(7 + (6 - (5 + 4)^{\wedge} - 3))^*2 + 1)$	-903873978	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7/(6/54)^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$
-861052518	$-9^{\wedge}8^*(7 + (6 + (5 + 4)^{\wedge} - 3))^*2 + 1)$	-903884373	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (7 + 65)^*4^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$
-861977588	$(-9 - 8)^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5)^*(432 - 1)$	-903885717	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (76 - 5)^*4^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$
-862050858	$(-9 - 8)^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5)^*(432 - 1)$	-903886977	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 76^*(5 - 4^{\wedge}3))^* - 21$
-863977519	$(-9 - 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)^*432 - 1)$	-903903189	$(9^{\wedge}8 + (7 - 65)^*4^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$
-863977553	$(-9 - 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)^*432 + 1)$	-903911610	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*(6 + 5)^*43)^* - 21$
-864050959	$(-9 - 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6 + 5)^*432 - 1)$	-903914256	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*65^*(4 + 3))^* - 21$
-864050993	$(-9 - 8)^*((7^{\wedge}6 + 5)^*432 + 1)$	-903922446	$(-9^{\wedge}8 + (7 + 6)^*5^*43)^*21$
-864310633	$((9 + 8)/(7 - (6^{\wedge}5/4)^{\wedge}3^*2))^{\wedge} - 1$	-903925281	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76^*5^*(4 + 3))^* - 21$
-865006823	$98 - ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1)$	-903930867	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*6^*(5 + 4 + 3))^* - 21$
-865006848	$9^*(8 - ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4/3)^{\wedge}2) + 1$	-903933072	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*(6^*5 + 4 + 3))^* - 21$
-865006850	$9^*(8 - ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4/3)^{\wedge}2) - 1$	-903933954	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*(6^*5 - 4 - 3))^* - 21$
-865006992	$-9^*(8 + ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4/3)^{\wedge}2) + 1$	-903936159	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*6^*(5 - 4 - 3))^* - 21$
-865006994	$-9^*(8 + ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4/3)^{\wedge}2) - 1$	-903936915	$(-9^{\wedge}8 + (7 + 6)^*5^*4^*3)^*21$
-865007019	$-98 - ((7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4)^{\wedge}(3 - 2 + 1)$	-903936978	$(9^{\wedge}8 - (76 + 5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^* - 21$
-865477560	$-9/((8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4)/3)^{\wedge} - 2 + 1$	-903938049	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76^*(5 + 4)^*3)^* - 21$
-865477562	$-9/((8 + (7^{\wedge}6 - 5)/4)/3)^{\wedge} - 2 - 1$	-903938805	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*6^*(5 + 4 + 3))^* - 21$
-865977484	$(-9 - 8)^*(7^{\wedge}6 - 5)^*(432 + 1)$	-903942480	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*(65^*4 + 3))^* - 21$
-866051094	$(-9 - 8)^*(7^{\wedge}6 + 5)^*(432 + 1)$	-903944433	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76^*(5^*4 + 3))^* - 21$
-870614934	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*(65 - 4)^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$	-903946554	$(9^{\wedge}8 + (76 - 5^{\wedge}4)^*3)^* - 21$
-872229141	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*(6 + 54)^{\wedge}3)^* - 21$	-903947625	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 7^*6^*(5 - 4 + 3))^* - 21$
-874014404	$(-9 - 8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5 + 432) - 1)$	-903948654	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*(6 + 5^*4 + 3))^* - 21$
-874014438	$(-9 - 8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5 + 432) + 1)$	-903950418	$(9^{\wedge}8 + 7^*(6 - 5^*4 + 3))^* - 21$
-876249654	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5 - 43))^*2 + 1$	-903950712	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*(65 + 4)^*3)^* - 21$
-876249850	$98^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5 - 43))^*2 - 1$	-903952224	$(-9^{\wedge}8 + (7^*65 + 4)^*3)^*21$
-880648200	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^{\wedge}6^*54)^*(- 3 - 21)$	-903952728	$(-9^{\wedge}8 + (7^*65 - 4)^*3)^*21$
-882448453	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 7^*65)^*(- 43/2 + 1)$	-903954009	$(9^{\wedge}8 - 76^*(5^*4 - 3))^* - 21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-903954240	$(9^8 - 7 * (65 - 4) * 3) * -21$	-903982281	$(9^8 + 76 * 5 / (4 + 3)) * -21$
-903954681	$(9^8 - 7 * (6 + 54) * 3) * -21$	-903982765	$(9^8 - (7 - 65) * 4 / 3) * -21$
-903956445	$(9^8 - 7 * (6 + 54 * 3)) * -21$	-903982912	$(9^8 - (7 - 65 * 4) / 3) * -21$
-903957453	$(-9^8 + (76 * 5 - 4) * 3) * 21$	-903983129	$(9^8 + (76 - 5) * 4 / 3) * -21$
-903958209	$(9^8 + 7 * (6 - 54 * 3)) * -21$	-903983360	$(9^8 - (7 - 6 * 54) / 3) * -21$
-903959973	$(9^8 + 7 * (6 - 54) * 3) * -21$	-903983458	$(9^8 + (7 + 6 * 54) / 3) * -21$
-903960288	$(-9^8 + (7 + 6 * 54) * 3) * 21$	-903983493	$(9^8 - 7 * (6 - 54) / 3) * -21$
-903960729	$(-9^8 + (76 + 5) * 4 * 3) * 21$	-903983773	$(9^8 + (76 * 5 - 4) / 3) * -21$
-903961170	$(9^8 + (7 - 6 * 54) * 3) * -21$	-903983829	$(9^8 + (76 * 5 + 4) / 3) * -21$
-903961989	$(9^8 - 76 * (5 + 4 + 3)) * -21$	-903984081	$(9^8 + 7 * (6 + 54) / 3) * -21$
-903962178	$(9^8 - 7 * (65 + 4 * 3)) * -21$	-903984130	$(9^8 + 7 * (65 - 4) / 3) * -21$
-903962997	$(-9^8 + (7 + 65) * 4 * 3) * 21$	-903984298	$(9^8 + (7 * 65 - 4) / 3) * -21$
-903963249	$(-9^8 + (76 - 5) * 4 * 3) * 21$	-903984333	$(9^8 - 76 * (5 - 4 - 3)) * -21$
-903964320	$(-9^8 + (7 + 65 * 4) * 3) * 21$	-903984480	$(9^8 - (7 - 6 - 54) * 3) * -21$
-903965202	$(9^8 + (7 - 65 * 4) * 3) * -21$	-903984606	$(9^8 + (7 - 6 + 54) * 3) * -21$
-903965580	$(9^8 - (7 + 6) * (54 + 3)) * -21$	-903984942	$(9^8 + (7 + 6 * 5) / 43) * -21$
-903966525	$(9^8 + (7 - 65) * 4 * 3) * -21$	-903985362	$(9^8 + (76 - 5 - 4) * 3) * -21$
-903967218	$(9^8 - (7 + 6) * (54 - 3)) * -21$	-903985845	$(9^8 - 7 * (6 + 5 - 43)) * -21$
-903968037	$(9^8 - (7 + 6) * (5 + 43)) * -21$	-903986048	$(9^8 + (76 + 5 * 4) / 3) * -21$
-903968401	$(9^8 - 7 * 65 * 4 / 3) * -21$	-903986055	$(9^8 + (7 + 6) * 54 / 3) * -21$
-903969234	$(9^8 - (76 + 5) * (4 + 3)) * -21$	-903986496	$(9^8 + (76 + 5 + 4) * 3) * -21$
-903969969	$(9^8 + 76 * (5 - 4 * 3)) * -21$	-903986993	$(9^8 + 76 * (5 - 4 / 3)) * -21$
-903970410	$(9^8 - 7 * (6 * 5 + 43)) * -21$	-903987189	$(9^8 + (7 * 6 + 54) * 3) * -21$
-903970501	$(9^8 - 76 * 5 * 4 / 3) * -21$	-903987525	$(9^8 + 76 * (5 - 4 + 3)) * -21$
-903970704	$(9^8 - (76 - 5) * (4 + 3)) * -21$	-903987609	$(9^8 + 7 * (6 - 5 + 43)) * -21$
-903970767	$(9^8 + (7 + 6) * (5 - 43)) * -21$	-903987924	$(9^8 + 76 * (5 / 4 + 3)) * -21$
-903971033	$(9^8 - 76 * (5 + 4 / 3)) * -21$	-903989667	$(9^8 + 7 * (65 - 4 - 3)) * -21$
-903971390	$(9^8 - 7 * (65 + 4 / 3)) * -21$	-903990500	$(9^8 + 7 * (65 - 4 / 3)) * -21$
-903971782	$(9^8 - 7 * (65 - 4 / 3)) * -21$	-903990892	$(9^8 + 7 * (65 + 4 / 3)) * -21$
-903972615	$(9^8 - 7 * (65 - 4 - 3)) * -21$	-903991249	$(9^8 + 76 * (5 + 4 / 3)) * -21$
-903974358	$(9^8 - 76 * (5 / 4 + 3)) * -21$	-903991515	$(9^8 - (7 + 6) * (5 - 43)) * -21$
-903974673	$(9^8 - 7 * (6 - 5 + 43)) * -21$	-903991578	$(9^8 + (76 - 5) * (4 + 3)) * -21$
-903974757	$(9^8 - 76 * (5 - 4 + 3)) * -21$	-903991781	$(9^8 + 76 * 5 * 4 / 3) * -21$
-903975093	$(-9^8 + (7 * 6 + 54) * 3) * 21$	-903991872	$(9^8 + 7 * (6 * 5 + 43)) * -21$
-903975289	$(9^8 - 76 * (5 - 4 / 3)) * -21$	-903992313	$(9^8 - 76 * (5 - 4 * 3)) * -21$
-903975786	$(9^8 - (76 + 5 + 4) * 3) * -21$	-903993048	$(9^8 + (76 + 5) * (4 + 3)) * -21$
-903976227	$(9^8 - (7 + 6) * 54 / 3) * -21$	-903993881	$(9^8 + 7 * 65 * 4 / 3) * -21$
-903976234	$(9^8 - (76 + 5 * 4) / 3) * -21$	-903994245	$(9^8 + (7 + 6) * (5 + 43)) * -21$
-903976437	$(9^8 + 7 * (6 + 5 - 43)) * -21$	-903995064	$(9^8 + (7 + 6) * (54 - 3)) * -21$
-903976920	$(9^8 - (76 - 5 - 4) * 3) * -21$	-903995757	$(-9^8 + (7 - 65) * 4 * 3) * 21$
-903977340	$(9^8 - (7 + 6 * 5) / 43) * -21$	-903996702	$(9^8 + (7 + 6) * (54 + 3)) * -21$
-903977676	$(9^8 - (7 - 6 + 54) * 3) * -21$	-903997080	$(-9^8 + (7 - 65 * 4) * 3) * 21$
-903977802	$(9^8 + (7 - 6 - 54) * 3) * -21$	-903997962	$(9^8 + (7 + 65 * 4) * 3) * -21$
-903977949	$(9^8 + 76 * (5 - 4 - 3)) * -21$	-903999033	$(9^8 + (76 - 5) * 4 * 3) * -21$
-903977984	$(9^8 - (7 * 65 - 4) / 3) * -21$	-903999285	$(9^8 + (7 + 65) * 4 * 3) * -21$
-903978152	$(9^8 - 7 * (65 - 4) / 3) * -21$	-904000104	$(9^8 + 7 * (65 + 4 * 3)) * -21$
-903978201	$(9^8 - 7 * (6 + 54) / 3) * -21$	-904000293	$(9^8 + 76 * (5 + 4 + 3)) * -21$
-903978453	$(9^8 - (76 * 5 + 4) / 3) * -21$	-904001112	$(-9^8 + (7 - 6 * 54) * 3) * 21$
-903978509	$(9^8 - (76 * 5 - 4) / 3) * -21$	-904001553	$(9^8 + (76 + 5) * 4 * 3) * -21$
-903978789	$(9^8 + 7 * (6 - 54) / 3) * -21$	-904001994	$(9^8 + (7 + 6 * 54) * 3) * -21$
-903978824	$(9^8 - (7 + 6 * 54) / 3) * -21$	-904002309	$(9^8 - 7 * (6 - 54) * 3) * -21$
-903978922	$(9^8 + (7 - 6 * 54) / 3) * -21$	-904004073	$(9^8 - 7 * (6 - 54 * 3)) * -21$
-903979153	$(9^8 - (76 - 5) * 4 / 3) * -21$	-904004829	$(9^8 + (76 * 5 - 4) * 3) * -21$
-903979370	$(9^8 + (7 - 65 * 4) / 3) * -21$	-904005837	$(9^8 + 7 * (6 + 54 * 3)) * -21$
-903979517	$(9^8 + (7 - 65) * 4 / 3) * -21$	-904007601	$(9^8 + 7 * (6 + 54) * 3) * -21$
-903980001	$(9^8 - 76 * 5 / (4 + 3)) * -21$	-904008042	$(9^8 + 7 * (65 - 4) * 3) * -21$
-903980476	$(9^8 - 76 * 5 / 4 / 3) * -21$	-904008273	$(9^8 + 76 * (5 * 4 - 3)) * -21$
-903980546	$(9^8 - (76 + 5 + 4) / 3) * -21$	-904009554	$(9^8 + (7 * 65 - 4) * 3) * -21$
-903980665	$(9^8 - (7 + 65 - 4) / 3) * -21$	-904010058	$(9^8 + (7 * 65 + 4) * 3) * -21$
-903980672	$(9^8 - (76 - 5 - 4) / 3) * -21$	-904011570	$(9^8 + 7 * (65 + 4) * 3) * -21$
-903980693	$(9^8 - (7 + 6 / 54) * 3) * -21$	-904011864	$(9^8 - 7 * (6 - 5 * 43)) * -21$
-903980749	$(9^8 - (76 - 5 * 4) / 3) * -21$	-904013628	$(9^8 + 7 * (6 + 5 * 43)) * -21$
-903980770	$(9^8 + (7 - 6 - 54) / 3) * -21$	-904014657	$(9^8 - 7 * 6 * (5 - 43)) * -21$
-903980928	$(9^8 - (76 - 5) / (4 + 3)) * -21$	-904015728	$(-9^8 + (76 - 5 * 4) * 3) * 21$
-903981354	$(9^8 + (76 - 5) / (4 + 3)) * -21$	-904017849	$(9^8 + 76 * (5 * 4 + 3)) * -21$
-903981512	$(9^8 - (7 - 6 - 54) / 3) * -21$	-904019802	$(9^8 + 7 * (65 * 4 + 3)) * -21$
-903981533	$(9^8 + (76 - 5 * 4) / 3) * -21$	-904023477	$(9^8 + 7 * 6 * (5 + 43)) * -21$
-903981589	$(9^8 + (7 + 6 / 54) * 3) * -21$	-904024233	$(9^8 + 76 * (5 + 4) * 3) * -21$
-903981610	$(9^8 + (7 + 6 + 54) / 3) * -21$	-904025304	$(9^8 + (76 + 5 * 4) * 3) * -21$
-903981617	$(9^8 + (7 + 65 - 4) / 3) * -21$	-904025367	$(9^8 + (7 + 6) * 54 * 3) * -21$
-903981736	$(9^8 + (76 + 5 + 4) / 3) * -21$	-904026123	$(9^8 + 7 * 6 * (54 - 3)) * -21$
-903981806	$(9^8 + 76 * 5 / 4 / 3) * -21$	-904028328	$(9^8 + 7 * (6 * 54 - 3)) * -21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-904029210	$(9^8+7*(6*54+3))^*-21$	-947027929	$((9^8+7)*(-6-5)+43)^*2+1$
-904031415	$(9^8+7*6*(54+3))^*-21$	-947027931	$((9^8+7)*(-6-5)+43)^*2-1$
-904037001	$(9^8+76*5*(4+3))^*-21$	-947028101	$((9^8+7)*(-6-5)-43)^*2+1$
-904039836	$(9^8+(7+6)*5*43)^*-21$	-947028103	$((9^8+7)*(-6-5)-43)^*2-1$
-904048026	$(9^8+7*65*(4+3))^*-21$	-948452463	$(9^8+7^8*54/3)^*-21$
-904050672	$(9^8+7*(6+5)*43)^*-21$	-950839146	$9*(8+7^8*(5-43*21))$
-904059093	$(9^8-(7-65)*4^3)^*-21$	-950839290	$9*(-8+7^8*(5-43*21))$
-904075305	$(9^8-76*(5-4^3))^*-21$	-952271964	$(9^8+7*(65+4)^3)^*-21$
-904076565	$(9^8+(76-5)*4^3)^*-21$	-953133237	$(9^8+7*6^5*43)^*-21$
-904077909	$(9^8+(7+65)*4^3)^*-21$	-954200511	$9-8*7*65*(4^3*2-1)$
-904088304	$(9^8+7/(6/54)^3)^*-21$	-954204143	$9-8*(7*65*4^3*2-1)$
-904090005	$(9^8+(76+5)*4^3)^*-21$	-954204159	$9-8*(7*65*4^3*2+1)$
-904091265	$(9^8+76*(5+4^3))^*-21$	-954204161	$-9-8*(7*65*4^3*2-1)$
-904313641	$(9^8+76*5^4/3)^*-21$	-954204177	$-9-8*(7*65*4^3*2+1)$
-904491861	$(9^8+76*5*4^3)^*-21$	-954204207	$9-8*7*(65*4^3*2+1)$
-904592661	$(9^8+7*65*4^3)^*-21$	-954207791	$9-8*7*65*(4^3*2+1)$
-904804306	$(9^8+(7^8-54)/3)^*-21$	-956091276	$9*(8-(7^8-5)*43)^*21$
-904805062	$(9^8+(7^8+54)/3)^*-21$	-956092716	$9*(8-(7^8-5)*43*21)$
-904973853	$(9^8+76*(5^4-3))^*-21$	-956092860	$-9*(8+(7^8-5)*43*21)$
-904983429	$(9^8+76*(5^4+3))^*-21$	-956094300	$-9*(8+(7^8-5)*43)^*21$
-905117892	$(9^8+7*(6^5-43))^*-21$	-956172546	$9*(8-(7^8+5)*43)^*21$
-905130534	$(9^8+7*(6^5+43))^*-21$	-956173986	$9*(8-(7^8+5)*43*21)$
-905144625	$(9^8+76*(5+4)^3)^*-21$	-956174130	$-9*(8+(7^8+5)*43*21)$
-906973641	$(9^8+76*5^4*3)^*-21$	-956175570	$-9*(8+(7^8+5)*43)^*21$
-907839009	$(9^8+7/6*5^4)^3)^*-21$	-961427556	$9*(8-7^8*(5+43*21))$
-909232128	$(9^8+(7/6*54)^3)^*-21$	-961427700	$-9*(8+7^8*(5+43*21))$
-909362129	$(9^8+7)*(-6/(5+43)-21)$	-968540985	$(9^8-7*65)*(-43/2-1)$
-910108223	$-9*(8*(7+6*5^4/3))^2+1$	-968561460	$(9^8+7*65)*(-43/2-1)$
-910108225	$-9*(8*(7+6*5^4/3))^2-1$	-973440639	$9^8-7^8*5*(4^3)^2+1$
-911389626	$(9^8+(7^8-54)^3)^*-21$	-976561891	$9+8*(76-(5^4)^3/2-1)$
-911396430	$(9^8+(7^8+54)^3)^*-21$	-976563107	$9-8*(76+(5^4)^3/2+1)$
-914838462	$(-9+8*7^8*54)^*(3-21)$	-983196613	$(9^8+(7-65)^4/3)^*-21$
-916749141	$(9^8+76*(5^4)^3)^*-21$	-990073299	$9^8*(7-6*5)+4*321$
-920238165	$(9^8+7/6*(6-54)^3)^*-21$	-990073680	$9^8*(7-6*5)+43*21$
-921986016	$(9^8+(76*5/4)^3)^*-21$	-990075486	$9^8*(7-6*5)-43*21$
-923113017	$9^8/(-7*6+5*(4+3^2-2))^{\wedge-1}$	-990075867	$9^8*(7-6*5)-4*321$
-924234948	$9^8*((-7*6/54)^3-21)$	-992436444	$98-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge(3+2)+1}$
-926301663	$9^8*7/6*(5*(-4+3^2-2)+1)$	-992436445	$98-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge(3+2)}*1$
-935733141	$(9^8+7*(6+54)^3)^*-21$	-992436446	$98-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge(3+2)-1}$
-935853961	$(9+8)*7*(6*5*4^3*2+1)$	-992436640	$-98-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge(3+2)+1}$
-935854063	$(-9-8)*(7*6*5*4^3*2-1)$	-992436641	$-98-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge(3+2)}*1$
-935854097	$(-9-8)*(7*6*5*4^3*2+1)$	-992436642	$-98-(7/(6/54))^{\wedge(3+2)-1}$
-935854199	$(9+8)*-7*(6*5*4^3*2+1)$	-997002990	$9+(876-5^4*3)^{\wedge(2+1)}$
-937347348	$(9^8+7*(65-4)^3)^*-21$	-997003008	$-9+(876-5^4*3)^{\wedge(2+1)}$
-938721273	$98-7^8*(5^4)^3-21$	-997865043	$(9^8-7^8*(5-43))^*-21$
-938721469	$-98-7^8*(5^4)^3-21$	-1001663514	$9*(8-7^8*(5^4+321))$
-940838955	$98-7^8*(5^4)^3-2-1$	-1001663658	$-9*(8+7^8*(5^4+321))$
-940838981	$9*8-7^8*(5^4)^3-2-1$	-1002829167	$9^8*((-7+6/54)/3-21)$
-940839125	$9*-8-7^8*(5^4)^3-2-1$	-1008016623	$9-8*7^8*(54-3)^*21$
-940839151	$-98-7^8*(5^4)^3-2-1$	-1008016641	$-9-8*7^8*(54-3)^*21$
-941074253	$98-7^8*(5^4)^3-2+1$	-1010213673	$(9^8+(7^8-5)*43)^*-21$
-941074279	$9*8-7^8*(5^4)^3-2+1$	-1010222703	$(9^8+(7^8+5)*43)^*-21$
-941074423	$9*-8-7^8*(5^4)^3-2+1$	-1010800782	$-9^{\wedge(8-7+6)}*(5^4/3+2+1)$
-941074449	$-98-7^8*(5^4)^3-2+1$	-1015583751	$9^8*8-7-(6*54)^3*21$
-941191881	$98-7^8*(5^4)^3+21$	-1016487262	$98-7^8*5*(4^3)^{\wedge(2+1)}$
-941191923	$98-7^8*(5^4)^3-21$	-1016487458	$-98-7^8*5*(4^3)^{\wedge(2+1)}$
-941192077	$-98-7^8*(5^4)^3+21$	-1021193311	$9-8*7^8*(543*2-1)$
-941192119	$-98-7^8*(5^4)^3-21$	-1021193329	$-9-8*7^8*(543*2-1)$
-941309551	$98-7^8*(5^4)^3+2-1$	-1022571333	$(9^8+7^8*(5+43))^*-21$
-941309577	$9*8-7^8*(5^4)^3+2-1$	-1023075695	$9-8*7^8*(543*2+1)$
-941309721	$9*-8-7^8*(5^4)^3+2-1$	-1023075713	$-9-8*7^8*(543*2+1)$
-941309747	$-98-7^8*(5^4)^3+2-1$	-1026289053	$9*(87*(6-5*4^3*2)+1)$
-941544849	$98-7^8*(5^4)^3+2+1$	-1026289071	$9*(87*(6-5*4^3*2)-1)$
-941544875	$9*8-7^8*(5^4)^3+2+1$	-1028935467	$(9^8-(7-65^4)/3)^*-21$
-941545019	$9*-8-7^8*(5^4)^3+2+1$	-1028935565	$(9^8+(7+65^4)/3)^*-21$
-941545045	$-98-7^8*(5^4)^3+2+1$	-1029192156	$9*(-8+7^8*54)^*(3-21)$
-943662531	$98-7^8*(5^4)^3+21$	-1029194748	$9*(8+7^8*54)^*(3-21)$
-943662727	$-98-7^8*(5^4)^3+21$	-1029983220	$(9^8+7^8*(54-3))^*-21$
-947027621	$((9^8-7)*(-6-5)+43)^*2+1$	-1031981304	$(9^8-76*5^4)^*(-3-21)$
-947027623	$((9^8-7)*(-6-5)+43)^*2-1$	-1033066872	$(9^8-7*6*54)^*(-3-21)$
-947027793	$((9^8-7)*(-6-5)-43)^*2+1$	-1033077624	$(9^8-7*65*4)^*(-3-21)$
-947027795	$((9^8-7)*(-6-5)-43)^*2-1$	-1033084824	$(9^8-76*5*4)^*(-3-21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1033104456	$(9^8 - (7+6)^*54)^*(-3-21)$	-1076169950	$(9^8 + 7^*(6+5))^*(4^3 * -2-1)$
-1033104888	$(9^8 - 76^*(5+4))^*(-3-21)$	-1076173275	$(9^8 + 7^*6^*5)^*(4^3 * -2-1)$
-1033109712	$(9^8 - 7^*(65+4))^*(-3-21)$	-1076187150	$(9^8 + 765)^*(-4^3 * 2-1)$
-1033111056	$(9^8 - 7^*(65-4))^*(-3-21)$	-1076286123	$9^8 * ((7+6+(5+4)^{-3})^{-2+1})$
-1033111224	$(9^8 - 7^*(6+54))^*(-3-21)$	-1076935662	$9^8 * ((-7-6)^*((5+4)^{-3+2})+1)$
-1033113240	$(9^8 + 7^*(6-54))^*(-3-21)$	-1079004598	$-98^*7^*(6^*(5+4^3 \wedge 2) - 1)$
-1033113528	$(9^8 - (76+5)^*4)^*(-3-21)$	-1079005186	$-98^*(7^*6^*(5+4^3 \wedge 2) - 1)$
-1033114392	$(9^8 - (7+65)^*4)^*(-3-21)$	-1079005382	$-98^*(7^*6^*(5+4^3 \wedge 2) + 1)$
-1033114488	$(9^8 - (76-5)^*4)^*(-3-21)$	-1079005970	$-98^*7^*(6^*(5+4^3 \wedge 2) + 1)$
-1033115736	$(9^8 + (7-65)^*4)^*(-3-21)$	-1081862908	$(9^8 + (76-5)^{\wedge 4/3})^* - 21$
-1033118574	$(9^8 - 7^*65/4)^*(-3-21)$	-1082017836	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * (543-2) - 1)$
-1033119024	$(9^8 - 76^*5/4)^*(-3-21)$	-1082017870	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 543-2) + 1$
-1033120818	$(9^8 - (76+5)/4)^*(-3-21)$	-1084253111	$9^*(8 - (7^{\wedge}(6/5)^*4)^{\wedge(3+2)}) + 1$
-1033120878	$(9^8 - (76-5)/4)^*(-3-21)$	-1084253113	$9^*(8 - (7^{\wedge}(6/5)^*4)^{\wedge(3+2)}) - 1$
-1033121730	$(9^8 + (76-5)/4)^*(-3-21)$	-1084253255	$-9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}(6/5)^*4)^{\wedge(3+2)}) + 1$
-1033121790	$(9^8 + (76+5)/4)^*(-3-21)$	-1084253257	$-9^*(8 + (7^{\wedge}(6/5)^*4)^{\wedge(3+2)}) - 1$
-1033123584	$(9^8 + 76^*5/4)^*(-3-21)$	-1086017868	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 543-2-1)$
-1033124034	$(9^8 + 7^*65/4)^*(-3-21)$	-1086017884	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 543-2) + 1$
-1033126872	$(9^8 - (7-65)^*4)^*(-3-21)$	-1086017885	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 543-2)^{\wedge 1}$
-1033128120	$(9^8 + (76-5)^*4)^*(-3-21)$	-1086017886	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 543-2) - 1$
-1033128216	$(9^8 + (7+65)^*4)^*(-3-21)$	-1086017902	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 543-2+1)$
-1033129080	$(9^8 + (76+5)^*4)^*(-3-21)$	-1086017936	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 543+2-1)$
-1033129368	$(9^8 - 7^*(6-54))^*(-3-21)$	-1086017952	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 543+2) + 1$
-1033131384	$(9^8 + 7^*(6+54))^*(-3-21)$	-1086017953	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 543+2)^{\wedge 1}$
-1033131552	$(9^8 + 7^*(65-4))^*(-3-21)$	-1086017954	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 543+2) - 1$
-1033132896	$(9^8 + 7^*(65+4))^*(-3-21)$	-1086017970	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 543+2+1)$
-1033137720	$(9^8 + 76^*(5+4))^*(-3-21)$	-1086895656	$(98 - 7^{\wedge 6} * 5)^*(43^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-1033138152	$(9^8 + (7+6)^*54)^*(-3-21)$	-1087061967	$9 + (8 - 7^{\wedge 6} * 5)^*(43^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-1033157784	$(9^8 + 76^*5^*4)^*(-3-21)$	-1087061985	$-9 + (8 - 7^{\wedge 6} * 5)^*(43^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-1033164984	$(9^8 + 7^*65^*4)^*(-3-21)$	-1087076662	$98 - 7^{\wedge 6} * 5^*(43^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-1033175736	$(9^8 + 7^*6^*54)^*(-3-21)$	-1087076858	$-98 - 7^{\wedge 6} * 5^*(43^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-1034261304	$(9^8 + 76^*5^{\wedge 4})^*(-3-21)$	-1087091535	$9 - (8 + 7^{\wedge 6} * 5)^*(43^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-1034715627	$9^8 * ((-7+6-5)^*4 - 3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$	-1087091553	$-9 - (8 + 7^{\wedge 6} * 5)^*(43^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-1037657124	$98^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 5 - 4)^*(3-21)$	-1087257864	$(-98 - 7^{\wedge 6} * 5)^*(43^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-1037671236	$98^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 5 + 4)^*(3-21)$	-1087547258	$98 - 7^{\wedge 6} * (5^*43^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-1042864389	$(9^8 + 7^*6^*54^{\wedge 3})^* - 21$	-1087547454	$-98 - 7^{\wedge 6} * (5^*43^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-1044806994	$(9^8 + 7^{\wedge 6} * (54+3))^* - 21$	-1087782556	$98 - 7^{\wedge 6} * (5^*43^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-1049193684	$-98^*(7^{\wedge 6} * (5+43^*2) - 1)$	-1087782752	$-98 - 7^{\wedge 6} * (5^*43^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-1049193880	$-98^*(7^{\wedge 6} * (5+43^*2) + 1)$	-1088071950	$(98 - 7^{\wedge 6} * 5)^*(43^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-1054605303	$9^*((8 - 7^*65)^*4^{\wedge 3 \wedge 2} + 1)$	-1088238441	$9 + (8 - 7^{\wedge 6} * 5)^*(43^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-1054605321	$9^*((8 - 7^*65)^*4^{\wedge 3 \wedge 2} - 1)$	-1088238459	$-9 + (8 - 7^{\wedge 6} * 5)^*(43^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-1055441826	$9^8 * (-7 - (6/5/4)^{-3/2+1})$	-1088253152	$98 - 7^{\wedge 6} * 5^*(43^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-1056964589	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*(4+3) - 2) + 1$	-1088253348	$-98 - 7^{\wedge 6} * 5^*(43^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-1056964591	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*(4+3) - 2) - 1$	-1088268041	$9 - (8 + 7^{\wedge 6} * 5)^*(43^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-1056964625	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*(4+3) + 2) + 1$	-1088268059	$-9 - (8 + 7^{\wedge 6} * 5)^*(43^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-1056964627	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*(4+3) + 2) - 1$	-1088434550	$(-98 - 7^{\wedge 6} * 5)^*(43^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-1067310216	$9^*(8 - 7^{\wedge 6} * (5+43))^*21$	-1090017968	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * (543+2) - 1)$
-1067311035	$(9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 54 - 3))^*21$	-1090018002	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge 6} * (543+2) + 1)$
-1067311215	$9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 54 - 3)^*21$	-1092098133	$(9^8 + (7+65)^{\wedge 4/3})^* - 21$
-1067311233	$9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 54 - 3)^*21$	-1092111255	$9^8 * (7 - 6^*5 - (4/3)^{\wedge(2+1)})$
-1067311413	$(-9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 54 - 3))^*21$	-1092588058	$(9 - 8^{\wedge 7/6})^*(5^{\wedge 4} * (3+2) + 1)$
-1067312043	$(9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 54 + 3))^*21$	-1092644326	$(-9 - 8^{\wedge 7/6})^*(5^{\wedge 4} * (3+2) + 1)$
-1067312223	$9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 54 + 3)^*21$	-1097072631	$-9^*((87+6)^*5^*4^{\wedge 3 \wedge 2} - 1)$
-1067312241	$-9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 54 + 3)^*21$	-1097072649	$-9^*((87+6)^*5^*4^{\wedge 3 \wedge 2} + 1)$
-1067312421	$(-9 - 8^*(7^{\wedge 6} * 54 + 3))^*21$	-1098632729	$9^*(8+7/6 - (5^{\wedge 4})^{\wedge 3/2}) + 1$
-1067313240	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge 6} * (5+43))^*21$	-1098632731	$9^*(8+7/6 - (5^{\wedge 4})^{\wedge 3/2}) - 1$
-1071378441	$(9 - 8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5))^*(4^{\wedge 3 \wedge 2} - 1)$	-1098632750	$9^*(8-7/6 - (5^{\wedge 4})^{\wedge 3/2}) + 1$
-1071386615	$(9 - 8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5))^*(4^{\wedge 3 \wedge 2} + 1)$	-1098632752	$9^*(8-7/6 - (5^{\wedge 4})^{\wedge 3/2}) - 1$
-1073475657	$-9^*(8+7^*65^*(4^{\wedge 3 \wedge 2} - 1))$	-1098632873	$9^*(-8+7/6 - (5^{\wedge 4})^{\wedge 3/2}) + 1$
-1073479743	$-9^*(8+7^*65^*(4^{\wedge 3 \wedge 2} - 1))$	-1098632875	$9^*(-8+7/6 - (5^{\wedge 4})^{\wedge 3/2}) - 1$
-1073479761	$-9^*(8+7^*65^*(4^{\wedge 3 \wedge 2} + 1))$	-1098632894	$9^*(-8-7/6 - (5^{\wedge 4})^{\wedge 3/2}) + 1$
-1073479815	$-9^*(8+7^*65^*(4^{\wedge 3 \wedge 2} + 1))$	-1098632896	$9^*(-8-7/6 - (5^{\wedge 4})^{\wedge 3/2}) - 1$
-1073483847	$-9^*(8+7^*65^*(4^{\wedge 3 \wedge 2} + 1))$	-1106841694	$-98^*(7^{\wedge 6} * (5+43))^*2-1$
-1075400388	$9^8 * ((7+6)^*((5+4)^{-3-2})+1)$	-1106841890	$-98^*(7^{\wedge 6} * (5+43))^*2+1$
-1076049927	$9^8 * ((-7-6+(5+4)^{-3})^*2+1)$	-1114431777	$9^8 * (7+6/54-32-1)$
-1076097015	$(9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5))^*(-4^{\wedge 3 \wedge 2} + 1)$	-1119842364	$-9^{\wedge}(8+7-6) - 5^{\wedge}(4^3)^*(2+1)$
-1076105225	$(9+8^{\wedge}(-7+6+5))^*(-4^{\wedge 3 \wedge 2} - 1)$	-1121513112	$-9^*((87-6^*5^{\wedge 4} * 3)^{\wedge 2} - 1)$
-1076148900	$(9^8 - 765)^*(-4^3 * 2 - 1)$	-1121513130	$-9^*((87-6^*5^{\wedge 4} * 3)^{\wedge 2} + 1)$
-1076162775	$(9^8 - 7^*6^*5)^*(4^3 * -2-1)$	-1134017199	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge 6} * (54-3))^*21$
-1076166100	$(9^8 - 7^*(6+5))^*(4^3 * -2-1)$	-1134018639	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge 6} * (54-3))^*21$
-1076167815	$(9^8 - 7^*6/5)^*(4^3 * -2-1)$	-1134018783	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge 6} * (54-3))^*21$
-1076168235	$(9^8 + 7^*6/5)^*(4^3 * -2-1)$	-1134020223	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge 6} * (54-3))^*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1136389905	$(9-876)*5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-1176019306	$-98*(7^6*(54-3)*2-1)$
-1136393373	$(9-876)*(5*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-1176019502	$-98*(7^6*(54-3)*2+1)$
-1136395107	$(9-876)*(5*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-1176610353	$9^8*(-7-(65-4)/3)+21$
-1136398575	$(9-876)*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-1176610395	$9^8*(-7-(65-4)/3)-21$
-1137503925	$(9^8-7^6*54)*(-32+1)$	-1178580311	$9*(8-(7^6)^5-4^3\wedge 2)+1$
-1137645368	$9*(8-(7-6/5^{\wedge}4^3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-1178580313	$9*(8-(7^6)^5-4^3\wedge 2)-1$
-1137645370	$9*(8-(7-6/5^{\wedge}4^3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	-1178580455	$-9*(8+(7^6)^5+4^3\wedge 2)+1$
-1137645512	$-9*(8+(7-6*5^{\wedge}4^3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-1178580457	$-9*(8+(7^6)^5+4^3\wedge 2)-1$
-1137645514	$-9*(8+(7-6*5^{\wedge}4^3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	-1181184665	$(9-8*7^6)*((5^4+3)*2-1)$
-1140480368	$9*(8-(7+6/5^{\wedge}4^3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-1181207255	$(-9-8*7^6)*((5^4+3)*2-1)$
-1140480370	$9*(8-(7+6/5^{\wedge}4^3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	-1181784205	$-98*7^6*5*(43/2-1)$
-1140480512	$-9*(8+(7+6*5^{\wedge}4^3)^{\wedge}2)+1$	-1183067031	$(9-8*7^6)*((5^4+3)*2+1)$
-1140480514	$-9*(8+(7+6*5^{\wedge}4^3)^{\wedge}2)-1$	-1183089657	$(-9-8*7^6)*((5^4+3)*2+1)$
-1140505839	$9^8*-7-654^3*(2+1)$	-1185594408	$(9^8+7^6*54)*(-3-21)$
-1141535268	$9^8*(-7-(6/5/4)^{\wedge}3/2-1)$	-1197913116	$(9-(8+7)^6)*((5^4/3/2+1)$
-1145827053	$(9-876*5)*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-1197915009	$(9+(8+7)^6)*((5^4/-3/2-1)$
-1145835795	$(9-876*5)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-1200723615	$9*(8-7^6*54+3)*21$
-1148186331	$9-876*5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-1200724749	$9*(8-7^6*54-3)*21$
-1148186349	$-9-876*5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-1200725055	$9*(8-(7^6*54-3)*21)$
-1148189835	$9-876*(5*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-1200725199	$-9*(8+(7^6*54-3)*21)$
-1148189853	$-9-876*(5*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-1200726189	$9*(8-(7^6*54+3)*21)$
-1148191587	$9-876*(5*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-1200726333	$-9*(8+(7^6*54+3)*21)$
-1148191605	$-9-876*(5*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-1200726639	$-9*(8+7^6*54-3)*21$
-1148195091	$9-876*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-1200727773	$-9*(8+7^6*54+3)*21$
-1148195109	$-9-876*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-1204723456	$(9-8*7^6*5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
-1148842413	$9*(8-7^6*543*2-1)$	-1204728064	$(-9-8*7^6*5)*4^{\wedge}(3+2-1)$
-1148842557	$-9*(8+7^6*543*2-1)$	-1205249139	$9^8*(-7+(6/54)^{\wedge}3-21)$
-1149901173	$9*((8-7^6*543)*2+1)$	-1205367237	$9^8*(-7-(6/54)^{\wedge}3-21)$
-1149901191	$9*((8-7^6*543)*2-1)$	-1207435166	$-98*((7^6+5)*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-1149901245	$9*(8-7^6*543*2+1)$	-1207435362	$-98*((7^6+5)*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-1149901263	$9*(8-7^6*543*2-1)$	-1208436279	$(9-8*(7^6-5)*4)*321$
-1149901389	$-9*(8+7^6*543*2-1)$	-1208439159	$9-8*(7^6-5)*4*321$
-1149901407	$-9*(8+7^6*543*2+1)$	-1208439177	$-9-8*(7^6-5)*4*321$
-1149901461	$-9*((8+7^6*543)*2-1)$	-1208442057	$(-9-8*(7^6-5)*4)*321$
-1149901479	$-9*((8+7^6*543)*2+1)$	-1208481219	$(9-(8*7^6-5)*4)*321$
-1150545627	$(-9-876*5)*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-1208486997	$(9+(8*7^6-5)*4)*-321$
-1150544405	$(-9-876*5)*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-1208494059	$(9-(8*7^6+5)*4)*321$
-1150960095	$9*(8-7^6*543*2+1)$	-1208498937	$(9+(8*7^6+5)*4)*-321$
-1150960239	$-9*(8+7^6*543*2+1)$	-1208538999	$(9-8*(7^6+5)*4)*321$
-1152216387	$-9*((8*7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3-21)$	-1208541879	$9-8*(7^6+5)*4*321$
-1152216555	$9*(8*7/(6/-54))^{\wedge}3+21$	-1208541897	$-9-8*(7^6+5)*4*321$
-1152216597	$9*(8*7/(6/-54))^{\wedge}3-21$	-1208544777	$(-9-8*(7^6+5)*4)*321$
-1152216765	$-9*((8*7/(6/54))^{\wedge}3+21)$	-1210476498	$-98*(7^6*5-4^3)*21$
-1156748112	$-9*((87+6*5^{\wedge}4^3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1210593804	$-98*(7^6*5-4-3)*21$
-1159982775	$(-9-876)*5*(4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-1210605466	$-98*(7^6*5-4/3)*21$
-1159986315	$(-9-876)*(5*4^3\wedge 2-1)$	-1210606152	$-98*(7^6*5-4+3)*21$
-1159988085	$(-9-876)*(5*4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-1210610268	$-98*(7^6*5+4-3)*21$
-1159991625	$(-9-876)*5*(4^3\wedge 2+1)$	-1210610954	$-98*(7^6*5+4/3)*21$
-1161493830	$9^8*((7+6)*((5+4)^{\wedge}3-2)-1)$	-1210622616	$-98*(7^6*5+4+3)*21$
-1161848124	$9^8*(7*(-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3+2)+1)$	-1210739922	$-98*(7^6*5+4^3)*21$
-1162143369	$9^8*((-7-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)*2-1)$	-1210891275	$(9^8-7^6*54)*(-32-1)$
-1162249182	$(9^8-7^6*5)*(4-32+1)$	-1219756023	$-9*((87*6-5)*4^3\wedge 2-1)$
-1162251207	$(9^8-7^6*5)*(4-32+1)$	-1219756041	$-9*((87*6-5)*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-1162261429	$(9^8-7^6/54)*-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1219784616	$(9-8*7^6*54)*3+21$
-1162261433	$((9^8-7/6)*-54+3)/2+1$	-1219785048	$(-9-8*7^6*54)*3+21$
-1162261501	$((9^8+7/6)*-54-3)/2-1$	-1223059047	$-9/(8+7)*(6^5*4^3\wedge 2+1)$
-1162261505	$(9^8+76/54)*-3^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1226833407	$9*(8*(7-65*4^3\wedge 2)+1)$
-1162271727	$(9^8+76*5)*(4-32+1)$	-1226833425	$9*(8*(7-65*4^3\wedge 2)-1)$
-1162273752	$(9^8+7*65)*(4-32+1)$	-1227902613	$-98*7^6*(5*43/2-1)$
-1162379565	$9^8*((7+6+(5+4)^{\wedge}3)*-2-1)$	-1231575219	$-9*87*(6*(5+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$
-1163029104	$9^8*((-7-6)*((5+4)^{\wedge}3+2)-1)$	-1231575993	$9*(-87*6*(5+4^3\wedge 2)+1)$
-1166136879	$9+8*7^6*(5-4^3)*21$	-1231576011	$9*(-87*6*(5+4^3\wedge 2)-1)$
-1169890469	$(9-8*7^6)*((5^4-3)*2-1)$	-1231576785	$-9*87*(6*(5+4^3\wedge 2)+1)$
-1169912843	$(-9-8*7^6)*((5^4-3)*2-1)$	-1232020311	$(-9-8)*7^6*(5^4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-1171772835	$(9-8*7^6)*((5^4-3)*2+1)$	-1232020345	$(9+8)*7^6*(5^4+3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-1171795245	$(-9-8*7^6)*((5^4-3)*2+1)$	-1238020410	$(-9-8)*7^6*(5^4-3^{\wedge}2)-1$
-1173861719	$9*(8-(7*6)^5+4^3\wedge 2)+1$	-1238020444	$(-9-8)*7^6*(5^4-3^{\wedge}2)+1$
-1173861721	$9*(8-(7*6)^5+4^3\wedge 2)-1$	-1239258720	$(9^8+(7+6)^5*43)*-21$
-1173861863	$-9*(8+(7*6)^5-4^3\wedge 2)+1$	-1239432117	$-98*(7^6*5*43/2-1)$
-1173861865	$-9*(8+(7*6)^5-4^3\wedge 2)-1$	-1239432313	$-98*(7^6*5*43/2+1)$
-1175131884	$(9-(8+7)^6)*((5^4/3/2-1)$	-1240020443	$(-9-8)*7^6*(5^4-3-2)-1$
-1175133741	$(9+(8+7)^6)*((5^4/-3/2+1)$	-1240020477	$(-9-8)*7^6*(5^4-3-2)+1$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1243348983	$-9 * ((87 * 6 + 5) * 4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-1334378043	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - 7 * 6 * 5^4) * (-32 + 1)$
-1243349001	$-9 * ((87 * 6 + 5) * 4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	-1334391931	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - 7 * 65 * 4) * (-32 + 1)$
-1244020475	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 - 3) - 2 - 1)$	-1334401231	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - 76 * 5 * 4) * (-32 + 1)$
-1244020509	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 - 3) - 2 + 1)$	-1334426589	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - (7 + 6) * 5^4) * (-32 + 1)$
-1244020543	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 - 3) + 2 - 1)$	-1334427147	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - 76 * (5 + 4)) * (-32 + 1)$
-1244020577	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 - 3) + 2 + 1)$	-1334433378	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - 7 * (65 + 4)) * (-32 + 1)$
-1245196330	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge} 6 * 5^4 - 3) * 2 - 1)$	-1334435114	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - 7 * (65 - 4)) * (-32 + 1)$
-1245196526	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge} 6 * 5^4 - 3) * 2 + 1)$	-1334435331	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - 7 * (6 + 5^4)) * (-32 + 1)$
-1245197506	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge} 6 * 5^4 + 3) * 2 - 1)$	-1334437935	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 7 * (6 - 5^4)) * (-32 + 1)$
-1245197702	$-98 * ((7^{\wedge} 6 * 5^4 + 3) * 2 + 1)$	-1334438307	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - (76 + 5)) * 4 * (-32 + 1)$
-1247646402	$9^{\wedge} 8 / (7 - (6 - (5 + 4)^{\wedge} - 3)^{\wedge} 2)^{\wedge} - 1$	-1334439423	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - (7 + 65)) * 4 * (-32 + 1)$
-1247941566	$9^{\wedge} 8 * (7 * (-6 + (5 + 4)^{\wedge} - 3 + 2) - 1)$	-1334439547	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - (76 - 5)) * 4 * (-32 + 1)$
-1248020575	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 - 3 + 2) - 1)$	-1334441159	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + (7 - 65)) * 4 * (-32 + 1)$
-1248020609	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 - 3 + 2) + 1)$	-1334445406	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - 76 * 5 / 4) * (-32 + 1)$
-1248341714	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - 7 * 65) * (4 - 32 - 1)$	-1334446398	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - 7 / 6 * 5^4) * (-32 + 1)$
-1248343889	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - 76 * 5) * (4 - 32 - 1)$	-1334450304	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 7 / 6 * 5^4) * (-32 + 1)$
-1248365929	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 76 * 5) * (4 - 32 - 1)$	-1334451296	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 76 * 5 / 4) * (-32 + 1)$
-1248368104	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 7 * 65) * (4 - 32 - 1)$	-1334455543	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - (7 - 65)) * 4 * (-32 + 1)$
-1249734889	$(-9 - 8) * ((7 * 6)^{\wedge} 5 / (4 / 3)^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-1334457155	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + (76 - 5)) * 4 * (-32 + 1)$
-1249734923	$(-9 - 8) * ((7 * 6)^{\wedge} 5 / (4 / 3)^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	-1334457279	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + (7 + 65)) * 4 * (-32 + 1)$
-1249949232	$9^{\wedge} 8 * (7 - (6 / 5 / 4)^{\wedge} - 3 + 2 - 1)$	-1334458395	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + (76 + 5)) * 4 * (-32 + 1)$
-1252020641	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3 - 2) - 1)$	-1334458767	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - 7 * (6 - 5^4)) * (-32 + 1)$
-1252020675	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3 - 2) + 1)$	-1334461371	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 7 * (6 + 5^4)) * (-32 + 1)$
-1256020673	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3) - 2 - 1)$	-1334461588	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 7 * (65 - 4)) * (-32 + 1)$
-1256020707	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3) - 2 + 1)$	-1334463324	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 7 * (65 + 4)) * (-32 + 1)$
-1256020741	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3) + 2 - 1)$	-1334469555	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 76 * (5 + 4)) * (-32 + 1)$
-1256020775	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3) + 2 + 1)$	-1334470113	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + (7 + 6) * 5^4) * (-32 + 1)$
-1260020773	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3 + 2) - 1)$	-1334495471	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 76 * 5 * 4) * (-32 + 1)$
-1260020807	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3 + 2) + 1)$	-1334504771	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 7 * 65 * 4) * (-32 + 1)$
-1260256079	$9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge} 3 * 21)$	-1334518659	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 7 * 6 * 5^4) * (-32 + 1)$
-1260256097	$-9 + 8 * 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge} 3 * 21)$	-1335920851	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 76 * 5^{\wedge} 4) * (-32 + 1)$
-1262020806	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3 * 2) - 1)$	-1336042674	$9^{\wedge} 8 * (7 - (6 / 5 / 4)^{\wedge} - 3 - 2 + 1)$
-1262020840	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3 * 2) + 1)$	-1340080056	$-9 * 8 * ((76 - 5) * 4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$
-1264908279	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5) * 4^{\wedge} 3 * 21$	-1340080200	$-9 * 8 * ((76 - 5) * 4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$
-1264908297	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5) * 4^{\wedge} 3 * 21$	-1343225847	$9 * (8^{\wedge} 7 / (6 / (5 - 432))) + 1$
-1265015799	$9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5) * 4^{\wedge} 3 * 21$	-1343225865	$9 * (8^{\wedge} 7 / (6 / (5 - 432))) - 1$
-1265015817	$-9 - 8 * (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5) * 4^{\wedge} 3 * 21$	-1344014288	$9^{\wedge} 8 * (7 * 6 / 5^4 - 32) + 1$
-1267431165	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 + 3)) * 21$	-1344014290	$9^{\wedge} 8 * (7 * 6 / 5^4 - 32) - 1$
-1267432605	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 + 3) * 21)$	-1346368695	$(9 - 8^{\wedge} (7 + 6 - 5) / 4) * 321$
-1267432749	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 + 3) * 21)$	-1346374473	$(9 + 8^{\wedge} (7 + 6 - 5) / 4) * -321$
-1267434189	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 + 3)) * 21$	-1348468709	$(9 - 8^{\wedge} 7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 / 3)) * (2 + 1)$
-1268020905	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3^{\wedge} 2) - 1)$	-1348468763	$(-9 - 8^{\wedge} 7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 / 3)) * (2 + 1)$
-1268020939	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3^{\wedge} 2) + 1)$	-1354257567	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 - 4 * 321))$
-1269667999	$9 - 8 * 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge} 3 * 21)$	-1354257711	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 - 4 * 321))$
-1272971237	$(9 + 8^{\wedge} 7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge} 4 / 3)) * (2 + 1)$	-1359470952	$9 * (8 - (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5) * 4) * 321$
-1272971291	$(-9 + 8^{\wedge} 7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge} 4 / 3)) * (2 + 1)$	-1359493992	$9 * (8 - (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5) * 4 * 321)$
-1280021103	$(9 + 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * 5 / (4^{\wedge} - 3 / - 2) + 1)$	-1359494136	$-9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge} 6 - 5) * 4 * 321)$
-1280021137	$(-9 - 8) * (7^{\wedge} 6 * 5 / 4^{\wedge} - 3 * 2 + 1)$	-1359609552	$9 * (8 - (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5) * 4 * 321)$
-1281835692	$9^{\wedge} 8 * (7 * (-6 + 5) * (4 + 3^{\wedge} 2 - 2) - 1)$	-1359609696	$-9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5) * 4 * 321)$
-1304223039	$(9^{\wedge} 8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * 5^4 * 3) * - 21$	-1359632736	$-9 * (8 + (7^{\wedge} 6 + 5) * 4) * 321$
-1306525693	$(9 + 8^{\wedge} 7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)) / (2 + 1)$	-1360492938	$98 * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge} 3) * 2 + 1)$
-1306525699	$(-9 + 8^{\wedge} 7 * (6 - 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)) / (2 + 1)$	-1360493134	$98 * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge} 3) * 2 - 1)$
-1311903927	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge} 3) * 21)$	-1363787199	$9 - 8 * 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge} 3) * 21$
-1311904071	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge} 3) * 21)$	-1363787217	$-9 - 8 * 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 + 4^{\wedge} 3) * 21$
-1314374530	$-98 * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 + 3) * 2 - 1)$	-1364845977	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 + 4 * 321))$
-1314374726	$-98 * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 + 3) * 2 + 1)$	-1364846121	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 + 4 * 321))$
-1314914301	$(-9 - 8^{\wedge} 7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)) / (2 + 1)$	-1367017472	$(9 / - 8 * ((7^{\wedge} 6 - 5 + 4) / 3)^{\wedge} - 2)^{\wedge} - 1$
-1314914307	$(-9 - 8^{\wedge} 7 * (6 + 5^{\wedge} 4 * 3)) / (2 + 1)$	-1367929134	$9^{\wedge} 8 * (-7 * 6 / 5^4 - 32 + 1)$
-1317198131	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 - 3) * 2) + 1$	-1372256208	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge} 6 * 5^4) * (3 + 21)$
-1317198133	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 - 3) * 2) - 1$	-1372259664	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * 5^4) * (3 + 21)$
-1317198275	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 - 3) * 2) + 1$	-1372670408	$(9 / - 8 / (7 - (6 * 5 + 4)^{\wedge} 3)^{\wedge} 2)^{\wedge} - 1$
-1317198277	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 - 3) * 2) - 1$	-1375900749	$9^{\wedge} 8 * ((-7 - 6 + 5) * 4 + 3^{\wedge} (-2 - 1))$
-1329065010	$(9 - 87) * 65 * (4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-1383542832	$-98 * (7^{\wedge} 6 * 5 - 4) * (3 + 21)$
-1329070002	$(9 - 87) * (65 * 4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 - 1)$	-1383561648	$-98 * (7^{\wedge} 6 * 5 + 4) * (3 + 21)$
-1329070158	$(9 - 87) * (65 * 4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	-1407045152	$(-98 / ((7 + 6)^{\wedge} 5 + 43)^{\wedge} 2)^{\wedge} - 1$
-1329075150	$(9 - 87) * 65 * (4^{\wedge} 3^{\wedge} 2 + 1)$	-1409286072	$9 - (8^{\wedge} (7 + 6 - 5) * 4 - 3) * 21$
-1329665382	$9^{\wedge} 8 * (-7 + 6 / 5^4 - 3 - 21)$	-1409286198	$9 - (8^{\wedge} (7 + 6 - 5) * 4 + 3) * 21$
-1329904223	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3) * 2) + 1$	-1410975854	$9^{\wedge} 8 * (-7 * 6 / 5^4 - 32) + 1$
-1329904225	$9 * (8 - 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3) * 2) - 1$	-1410975856	$9^{\wedge} 8 * (-7 * 6 / 5^4 - 32) - 1$
-1329904367	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3) * 2) + 1$	-1417788027	$9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge} 3 * 21))$
-1329904369	$-9 * (8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5^{\wedge} 4 + 3) * 2) - 1$	-1417788171	$9 * (-8 + 7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 - 4^{\wedge} 3 * 21))$
-1332975851	$(9^{\wedge} 8 - 76 * 5^{\wedge} 4) * (-32 + 1)$	-1418140948	$98 * (7^{\wedge} 6 * (5 - 4 * 32) + 1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1418141144	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-4*32)-1)$	-1484777952	$(-9-87*65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1418974293	$(9^{\wedge}8-76*5^{\wedge}4)*(-32-1)$	-1484789280	$(-9-87*65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1420466949	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*6*54)*(-32-1)$	-1486873600	$(-9/((8+7)*(6^{\wedge}5-4^{\wedge}3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-1420481733	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*65*4)*(-32-1)$	-1490020812	$98*(7-65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1420491633	$(9^{\wedge}8-76*5*4)*(-32-1)$	-1490026398	$98*((7-65)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1420518627	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7+6)*54)*(-32-1)$	-1490026594	$98*(7-65)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1$
-1420519221	$(9^{\wedge}8-76*(5+4))*(-32-1)$	-1490032180	$98*(7-65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1420525854	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(65+4))*(-32-1)$	-1491786467	$(-9+8*7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4-321)$
-1420527702	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(65-4))*(-32-1)$	-1491789311	$9+8*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-321)$
-1420527933	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(6+54))*(-32-1)$	-1494663424	$-9*8^{\wedge}7-(6-5*4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1420530705	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*(6-54))*(-32-1)$	-1500512062	$98-7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-1420531101	$(9^{\wedge}8-(76+5)*4)*(-32-1)$	-1500512076	$98-7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-1420532289	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7+65)*4)*(-32-1)$	-1500512088	$9*8-7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-1420532421	$(9^{\wedge}8-(76-5)*4)*(-32-1)$	-1500512102	$9*8-7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-1420534137	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7-65)*4)*(-32-1)$	-1500512232	$-9*8-7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-1420538658	$(9^{\wedge}8-76*5/4)*(-32-1)$	-1500512246	$-9*8-7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-1420539714	$(9^{\wedge}8-7/6*54)*(-32-1)$	-1500512258	$-98-7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$
-1420541472	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*6+5+4)+321$	-1500512272	$-98-7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$
-1420542114	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*6+5+4)-321$	-1505040912	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*(6-5+4)+3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1420543872	$(9^{\wedge}8+7/6*54)*(-32-1)$	-1508229558	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(-6+5-4)-3^{\wedge}(-2-1))$
-1420544928	$(9^{\wedge}8+76*5/4)*(-32-1)$	-1510602879	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*321$
-1420549449	$(9^{\wedge}8-(7-65)*4)*(-32-1)$	-1510602897	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*321$
-1420551165	$(9^{\wedge}8+(76-5)*4)*(-32-1)$	-1510605777	$(-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5-4))*321$
-1420551297	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7+65)*4)*(-32-1)$	-1510620543	$(9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4))*321$
-1420552485	$(9^{\wedge}8+(76+5)*4)*(-32-1)$	-1510623423	$9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*321$
-1420552881	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(6-54))*(-32-1)$	-1510623441	$-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*321$
-1420555653	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*(6+54))*(-32-1)$	-1516323600	$(-9/((8+7)*(6^{\wedge}5+4*3))^{\wedge}2)^{\wedge}-1$
-1420555884	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*(65-4))*(-32-1)$	-1529434075	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+321)$
-1420557732	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*(65+4))*(-32-1)$	-1529436991	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321)$
-1420564365	$(9^{\wedge}8+76*(5+4))*(-32-1)$	-1529437009	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321)$
-1420564959	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7+6)*54)*(-32-1)$	-1529439925	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4+321)$
-1420591953	$(9^{\wedge}8+76*5*4)*(-32-1)$	-1531392777	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(-32+1)$
-1420601853	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*65*4)*(-32-1)$	-1533201741	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*543)*(2+1)$
-1420616637	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*6*54)*(-32-1)$	-1533201795	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*543)*(2+1)$
-1422109293	$(9^{\wedge}8+76*5^{\wedge}4)*(-32-1)$	-1533436968	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4*32)-1)$
-1422655479	$-9*((8*76-5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1533437164	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4*32)+1)$
-1422655497	$-9*((8*76-5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1534260537	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)*21)$
-1423021752	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^{\wedge}3*21)$	-1534260681	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)*21)$
-1423021896	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^{\wedge}3*21)$	-1536626733	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3)*21$
-1423142712	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^{\wedge}3*21)$	-1536626751	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6)*(5^{\wedge}4-3)*21$
-1423142856	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^{\wedge}3*21)$	-1536729180	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))*21$
-1425916422	$9^{\wedge}8*-7+65^{\wedge}4*-3*21$	-1536731061	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))*21$
-1428376437	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3*21))$	-1536731079	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))*21$
-1428376581	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3*21))$	-1536731140	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)*21$
-1434479256	$-9*8*(76*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-1536731336	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3)*21$
-1434479319	$-9*(8*76*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-1536731397	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))*21$
-1434479337	$-9*(8*76*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-1536731415	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))*21$
-1434479400	$-9*8*(76*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-1536733296	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))*-21$
-1435166376	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*5*43)*-21$	-1536835725	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))*21$
-1446248439	$-9*((8*76+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1536835743	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))*21$
-1446248457	$-9*((8*76+5)*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1538600624	$-9*(8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$
-1456914688	$9*8^{\wedge}7-(6-5*4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1538600626	$-9*(8+7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2-1$
-1457465439	$9^{\wedge}8-7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	-1540483928	$9*(8-(7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2)+1$
-1457465453	$9^{\wedge}8-7*((6+5)^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	-1540483930	$9*(8-(7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2)-1$
-1474337772	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*65^{\wedge}4)*(-3+21)$	-1540484072	$-9*(8+(7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2)+1$
-1475726238	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	-1540484074	$-9*(8+(7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2)-1$
-1475726434	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*4^{\wedge}3*2+1)$	-1542368528	$-9*(8-7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$
-1475788552	$9*8*7-(6-5*4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1542368530	$-9*(8-7*(6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2-1$
-1475788921	$9*(8+7)-(6-5*4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1543790105	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3*2)+1$
-1475789191	$-9*(8+7)-(6-5*4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1543790107	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3*2)-1$
-1475789560	$9*8*-7-(6-5*4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1543790249	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3*2)+1$
-1475851678	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6+5)*4^{\wedge}3*2-1)$	-1543790251	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5+4)^{\wedge}3*2)-1$
-1480059378	$(9-87*65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1550143224	$-9*8/7^{\wedge}6*(54*3+21)$
-1480070670	$(9-87*65)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1550575845	$(98-7)*-65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1482418656	$9-87*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1550581669	$(-98+7)*(65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1482418674	$-9-87*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1550581851	$(-98+7)*(65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1482424224	$9-87*(65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1550587675	$(98-7)*-65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1482424242	$-9-87*(65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1551011029	$((9+8)/(7-(6*5^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3/2))^{\wedge}-1$
-1482424398	$9-87*(65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1551449499	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)*21$
-1482424416	$-9-87*(65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1551449517	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6)*(5^{\wedge}4+3)*21$
-1482429966	$9-87*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1551552954	$(98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))*21$
-1482429984	$-9-87*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1551554835	$9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))*21$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1551554853	$-9+(8-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))*21$	-1677203847	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32+1)$
-1551554914	$98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)*21$	-1677204135	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*54*(32+1)$
-1551555110	$-98-7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3)*21$	-1677204153	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*54*(32+1)$
-1551555171	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))*21$	-1677204441	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32+1)$
-1551555189	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))*21$	-1678240161	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*5)*(4-321)$
-1551557070	$(98+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))*-21$	-1678262913	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-321))$
-1551660507	$9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))*21$	-1678263057	$9*(-8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-321))$
-1551660525	$-9-(8+7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))*21$	-1678285809	$9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-321))$
-1558433528	$-9*(8-7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$	-1679690859	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(65^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)*21$
-1558433530	$-9*(8-7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2-1$	-1685448000	$((-9-8)/(765^{\wedge}4)^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}(-2+1)$
-1560328928	$9*(8-(7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2)+1$	-1688388057	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*6-5*(4/3^{\wedge}2-1))$
-1560328930	$9*(8-(7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2)-1$	-1693702467	$9^{\wedge}8*(76/(5/43-2)+1)$
-1560329072	$-9*(8+(7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2)+1$	-1699405137	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*321$
-1560329074	$-9*(8+(7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2)-1$	-1699428177	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*321)$
-1562225624	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$	-1699428249	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*321$
-1562225626	$-9*(8+7*(6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2-1$	-1699428321	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*321)$
-1573037738	$9+(87-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1699451289	$9*(8-(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*321)$
-1573037756	$-9+(87-6*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1699451361	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5-4)*321$
-1575555129	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32-1)$	-1699451433	$-9*(8+(7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*321)$
-1575555399	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1)$	-1699474473	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5+4)*321$
-1575555417	$-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1)$	-1700000000	$(-9-8)*(7-6+5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1575555687	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32-1)$	-1717910600	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-1578106691	$(9-8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)*43)*21$	-1717910796	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-1578107069	$(-9-8^{\wedge}7/(6/5)*43)*21$	-1720060293	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(65^{\wedge}4-3))*21$
-1581966939	$((9^{\wedge}8*-7-6+5)/4+3)*21$	-1720061175	$(9^{\wedge}8-7*(65^{\wedge}4+3))*21$
-1591084978	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)*2-1)$	-1720593225	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321))$
-1591085174	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5+4^{\wedge}3)*2+1)$	-1720616553	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321))$
-1592727393	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*6+5)+4*321$	-1720616697	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321))$
-1592727774	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*6+5)+43*21$	-1720640025	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+321))$
-1592728356	$9^{\wedge}8*(7-(6+5)*4)+321$	-1721865795	$((9^{\wedge}8-76)*-5*4+3)*2-1$
-1592728998	$9^{\wedge}8*(7-(6+5)*4)-321$	-1724851773	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*543)*(2+1)$
-1592729580	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*6+5)-43*21$	-1724851917	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*543*(2+1))$
-1592729961	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*6+5)-4*321$	-1724852061	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*543*(2+1))$
-1601955873	$(9-8*765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1724852205	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*543*(2+1))$
-1601968095	$(9-8*765)*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1730749194	$-9/8*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}4)/3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-1602614580	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4*3)^{\wedge}2)+1)$	-1735950405	$(9^{\wedge}8+76^{\wedge}5/4^{\wedge}3)*-21$
-1602614776	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*(5-(4*3)^{\wedge}2)-1)$	-1742733312	$9/(8^{\wedge}7/(6+5*(4/3-21)))$
-1604315151	$9-8*765*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1752515271	$-9^{\wedge}8/(7+6^{\wedge}+5*4^{\wedge}3)^{\wedge}2-1$
-1604315169	$-9-8*765*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1753755300	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3/2))+1)$
-1604321263	$9-8*(765*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1756264245	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))*(2+1)$
-1604321297	$-9-8*(765*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1756264299	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4-3))*(2+1)$
-1604327391	$9-8*765*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1761894576	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3-2-1))$
-1604327409	$-9-8*765*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1761928272	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2-1))$
-1606674447	$(-9-8*765*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-1763776942	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2+1))$
-1606686705	$(-9-8*765*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-1763810674	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2+1))$
-1607812402	$-98*(7*6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)-1)$	-1764029106	$-98*7^{\wedge}6*(54-3)*(2+1)$
-1607813186	$-98*7*(6*5^{\wedge}4^{\wedge}(3/2)+1)$	-1764088875	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3*2))+1)$
-1614141193	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1764734901	$(9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4-3))*(2+1)$
-1614144182	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-32)+1)$	-1764734955	$(-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4-3))*(2+1)$
-1614144378	$98*(7^{\wedge}6*5*(4-32)-1)$	-1764735045	$(9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4+3))*(2+1)$
-1614147367	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*5*(4+3))^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-1764735099	$(-9-8*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4+3))*(2+1)$
-1616920389	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7-65)^{\wedge}4*3)*-21$	-1764797463	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3*2)+1)$
-1629398106	$9^{\wedge}8*7*(-6+(54/32)^{\wedge}(-1))$	-1764910458	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1)$
-1630192311	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^{\wedge}6*54)*(-32-1)$	-1764914994	$9^{\wedge}8*(7*(-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3*2))+1)$
-1635772320	$(-9-87)*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1764916128	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3*2))+1)$
-1635778464	$(-9-87)*(65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1764920664	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3-2))+1)$
-1635778656	$(-9-87)*(65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1765033659	$-9^{\wedge}8*(7*6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3*2)-1)$
-1635784800	$(-9-87)*65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1765659308	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2-1))$
-1643321232	$-9*8/7^{\wedge}6*(5*43-21)$	-1765693076	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2-1))$
-1660192030	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1765742247	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(-3*2))+1)$
-1660192226	$-98*((7^{\wedge}6-5)*(4*3)^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1767541674	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1))$
-1660333150	$-98*(7^{\wedge}6+5*(4*3)^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1767575478	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2+1))$
-1669850224	$98*(7-65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-1772497602	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54)*(32-1)$
-1669851596	$-98*(7+65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-1772499762	$9*(8-7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1))$
-1669856496	$98*(7-65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1772499906	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1))$
-1669856692	$98*(7-65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1772502066	$-9*(8+7^{\wedge}6*54*(32-1))$
-1669857182	$-98*((7+6)*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1773205701	$(9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))*(2+1)$
-1669857378	$-98*((7+6)*5*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1773205755	$(-9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4+3))*(2+1)$
-1669857868	$-98*(7+65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-1776075822	$9^{\wedge}8*(-7*6+5*4/3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1669858064	$-98*(7+65*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-1778661766	$(9^{\wedge}8+7*65^{\wedge}4/3)*-21$
-1669862964	$98*(7-65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-1779795909	$9^{\wedge}8*(76/(5/43-2)-1)$
-1669864336	$-98*(7+65*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1))$	-1784500023	$9-8*7^{\wedge}6*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1784500041	$-9 \cdot 8^7 \cdot 7^6 \cdot (5^4 \cdot 3 + 21)$	-1849688162	$-98^* ((7+65) \cdot 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$
-1785980259	$9^* (8-765)^* (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$	-1849695120	$-98^* (7+65)^* (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$
-1785987063	$9^* ((8-765)^* 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$	-1850182317	$9^8 \cdot 7^* (-6 + (5+4)^{-3} \cdot 2) - 1$
-1785987081	$9^* ((8-765)^* 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$	-1850300496	$-9^8 / (7 + (6 - (5+4)^{-3})^2)^{-1}$
-1785993885	$9^* (8-765)^* (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$	-1850890905	$9^8 \cdot 7^* (-7 \cdot 6 + (5+4)^{-3} \cdot 2 - 1)$
-1787076158	$-98^* (7^6 \cdot 5 - 4)^* (32 - 1)$	-1851003900	$9^8 \cdot 7^* (7^* (-6 + (5+4)^{-3} \cdot 2) - 1)$
-1787100462	$-98^* (7^6 \cdot 5 + 4)^* (32 - 1)$	-1851008436	$9^8 \cdot 7^* (7^* (-6 + (5+4)^{-3} \cdot 2) - 1)$
-1787776045	$(9 - 8^7 / 6)^5 \cdot (4^3 \cdot (3+2) - 1)$	-1851008682	$9^8 \cdot 7^* (-7^6 \cdot 5 + 4) + 321$
-1787812873	$(9 - 8^7 / (6/5))^* (4^3 \cdot (3+2) - 1)$	-1851009324	$9^8 \cdot 7^* (-7^6 \cdot 5 + 4) - 321$
-1787831287	$(-9 - 8^7 / (6/5))^* (4^3 \cdot (3+2) - 1)$	-1851009570	$9^8 \cdot 7^* (-7^* (6 + (5+4)^{-3} \cdot 2) - 1)$
-1787868115	$(9 + 8^7 / 6)^5 \cdot (-4^3 \cdot (3+2) + 1)$	-1851014106	$9^8 \cdot 7^* (-7^* (6 + (5+4)^{-3} \cdot 2) - 1)$
-1789125975	$(98+7)^* \cdot 65^* (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$	-1851127101	$-9^8 \cdot 7^* (7^6 + (5+4)^{-3} \cdot 2 + 1)$
-1789132695	$(-98-7)^* (65^* 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$	-1851717672	$-9^8 / (7 + (6 + (5+4)^{-3})^2)^{-1}$
-1789132905	$(-98-7)^* (65^* 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$	-1851835689	$9^8 \cdot 7^* (-7^* (6 + (5+4)^{-3} \cdot 2) - 1)$
-1789139625	$(98+7)^* \cdot 65^* (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$	-1855402329	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 - (5^4)^3 \cdot 21$
-1792336897	$-9^* (8 / (7^6))^{\wedge (5-4-3)} \cdot 2^{-1}$	-1862030723	$-98^* 7^6 \cdot (5^4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2^{\wedge -1})$
-1795101255	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^4 (4^3 \cdot 2 / 2) - 1$	-1862169264	$9^8 \cdot 7^* (6 + (5+4)^{-3} / 2) - 1$
-1795336553	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 \cdot 5^4 (4^3 \cdot 2 / 2) + 1$	-1867794642	$-98^* (7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3)^* (2+1)$
-1804854483	$9^* (8-765)^* (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$	-1867795475	$-98^* (7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2^{\wedge -1})$
-1804854627	$-9^* (8+765)^* (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$	-1867795573	$-98^* (7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3 + 2^{\wedge -1})$
-1804861359	$9^* (8-765)^* 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1$	-1867796406	$-98^* (7^6 \cdot 5^4 + 3)^* (2+1)$
-1804861367	$9^* (8-765)^* 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1$	-1872512571	$(9^8 - 7^* 65)^* (-43 \cdot 2^{\wedge -1})$
-1804861369	$9^* (8-765)^* 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1$	-1872552156	$(9^8 + 7^* 65)^* (-43 \cdot 2^{\wedge -1})$
-1804861377	$9^* (8-765)^* 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1$	-1873560325	$-98^* 7^6 \cdot (5^4 \cdot 3 + 2^{\wedge -1})$
-1804861503	$-9^* (8+765)^* 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1$	-1877449186	$9^8 + (7 - 6^5 \cdot 4 / 3)^{\wedge (2+1)}$
-1804861511	$-9^* (8+765)^* 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1$	-1882266253	$98 - 7^6 \cdot (5^4)^3 \cdot 2 - 1$
-1804861513	$-9^* (8+765)^* 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1$	-1882266279	$9^8 - 7^6 \cdot (5^4)^3 \cdot 2 - 1$
-1804861521	$-9^* (8+765)^* 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1$	-1882266449	$-98 - 7^6 \cdot (5^4)^3 \cdot 2 - 1$
-1804868253	$9^* (8-765)^* (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$	-1882501551	$98 - 7^6 \cdot (5^4)^3 \cdot 2 + 1$
-1804868397	$-9^* (8+765)^* (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$	-1882501577	$9^8 - 7^6 \cdot (5^4)^3 \cdot 2 + 1$
-1807943172	$(9^8 - 7^6 \cdot 65)^* (-43 + 2 - 1)$	-1882501747	$-98 - 7^6 \cdot (5^4)^3 \cdot 2 + 1$
-1807946322	$(9^8 - 76 \cdot 5)^* (-43 + 2 - 1)$	-1886852286	$9^* (8 - 7^6 \cdot 5^4)^* (32 + 1)$
-1807978242	$(9^8 + 76 \cdot 5)^* (-43 + 2 - 1)$	-1886854590	$9^* (8 - 7^6 \cdot 5^4)^* (32 + 1)$
-1807981392	$(9^8 + 7^6 \cdot 65)^* (-43 + 2 - 1)$	-1886854734	$-9^* (8 + 7^6 \cdot 5^4)^* (32 + 1)$
-1821206331	$-9^* (8 / 7^{\wedge -6} \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3 - 21)$	-1886857038	$-9^* (8 + 7^6 \cdot 5^4)^* (32 + 1)$
-1821206709	$-9^* (8 / 7^{\wedge -6} \cdot 5^4 \cdot 3 + 21)$	-1890854630	$-98^* (7^6 \cdot (5^4 \cdot 3 + 2) - 1)$
-1823728851	$-9^* (8+765)^* (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$	-1890854826	$-98^* (7^6 \cdot (5^4 \cdot 3 + 2) + 1)$
-1823735799	$-9^* ((8+765)^* 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$	-1894035704	$(9^8 - 7^* 65)^* (-43 \cdot 2 + 1)$
-1823735817	$-9^* ((8+765)^* 4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$	-1894039004	$(9^8 - 76 \cdot 5)^* (-43 \cdot 2 + 1)$
-1823742765	$-9^* (8+765)^* (4^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$	-1894072444	$(9^8 + 76 \cdot 5)^* (-43 \cdot 2 + 1)$
-1828618335	$9^* (8-7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 32 - 1)$	-1894075744	$(9^8 + 7^6 \cdot 65)^* (-43 \cdot 2 + 1)$
-1828618479	$-9^* (8+7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 32 - 1)$	-1894469067	$9^8 / (7 - 7^* (6 + (5+4)^{-3}) - 2)^{-1}$
-1829466305	$(9^8 - 7^6 \cdot 65)^* (-43 + 2^{\wedge -1})$	-1902371394	$-98^* (7^6 \cdot 5^4 - 4)^* (32 + 1)$
-1829504980	$(9^8 + 7^6 \cdot 65)^* (-43 + 2^{\wedge -1})$	-1902397266	$-98^* (7^6 \cdot 5^4 + 4)^* (32 + 1)$
-1829674935	$9^* ((8 - 7^6 \cdot 5^4) \cdot 32 + 1)$	-1907252163	$(9^8 + (7^6 \cdot 5^4)^3)^* (-2 - 1)$
-1829674953	$9^* ((8 - 7^6 \cdot 5^4) \cdot 32 - 1)$	-1920495809	$98 + (7 - 6^5 \cdot 4 / 3)^{\wedge (2+1)}$
-1829677167	$9^* (8 - 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 32 + 1)$	-1920495835	$9^8 + (7 - 6^5 \cdot 4 / 3)^{\wedge (2+1)}$
-1829677329	$-9^* (8 + 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 32 + 1)$	-1920495979	$-9^* 8 + (7 - 6^5 \cdot 4 / 3)^{\wedge (2+1)}$
-1829679543	$-9^* ((8 + 7^6 \cdot 5^4) \cdot 32 - 1)$	-1920496005	$-98 + (7 - 6^5 \cdot 4 / 3)^{\wedge (2+1)}$
-1829679561	$-9^* ((8 + 7^6 \cdot 5^4) \cdot 32 + 1)$	-1926972873	$98 + 7^6 \cdot 6^* (5 - 4^{\wedge (3 \cdot 2 + 1)})$
-1830736017	$9^* (8 - 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 32 + 1)$	-1926972899	$9^8 + 7^6 \cdot 6^* (5 - 4^{\wedge (3 \cdot 2 + 1)})$
-1830736161	$-9^* (8 + 7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 32 + 1)$	-1926973043	$-9^* 8 + 7^6 \cdot 6^* (5 - 4^{\wedge (3 \cdot 2 + 1)})$
-1835157033	$-9^* 8^7 \cdot (6^5 \cdot 4^{\wedge (3/2)} + 1)$	-1928149363	$98 - 7^6 \cdot 6^* (5 + 4^{\wedge (3 \cdot 2 + 1)})$
-1838147878	$98 - 7^6 \cdot 5^4 (4^3 \cdot 2 / 2) - 1$	-1928149389	$9^8 - 7^6 \cdot 6^* (5 + 4^{\wedge (3 \cdot 2 + 1)})$
-1838147904	$9^8 - 7^6 \cdot 6^* ((5^4)^{\wedge (3/2)} - 1)$	-1928149533	$9^* - 8 - 7^6 \cdot 6^* (5 + 4^{\wedge (3 \cdot 2 + 1)})$
-1838148048	$-9^* 8 - 7^6 \cdot 6^* ((5^4)^{\wedge (3/2)} - 1)$	-1928149559	$-98 - 7^6 \cdot 6^* (5 + 4^{\wedge (3 \cdot 2 + 1)})$
-1838148074	$-98 - 7^6 \cdot 6^* (5^{\wedge (4 \cdot 3/2)} - 1)$	-1929229137	$9^* (87 - (6+5)^4 \cdot 4^{\wedge (3/2)} + 1)$
-1838383176	$98 - 7^6 \cdot 6^* (5^{\wedge (4 \cdot 3/2)} + 1)$	-1929229155	$9^* (87 - (6+5)^4 \cdot 4^{\wedge (3/2)} - 1)$
-1838383202	$9^8 - 7^6 \cdot 6^* ((5^4)^{\wedge (3/2)} + 1)$	-1929230703	$-9^* (87 + (6+5)^4 \cdot 4^{\wedge (3/2)} - 1)$
-1838383346	$-9^* 8 - 7^6 \cdot 6^* ((5^4)^{\wedge (3/2)} + 1)$	-1929230721	$-9^* (87 + (6+5)^4 \cdot 4^{\wedge (3/2)} + 1)$
-1838383372	$-98 - 7^6 \cdot 6^* (5^{\wedge (4 \cdot 3/2)} + 1)$	-1934250632	$9^8 \cdot 7^6 - (6^5 \cdot 4 / 3)^{\wedge (2+1)}$
-1839219630	$9^8 - 7^6 \cdot 6^* ((5^4)^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$	-1935296063	$-9 / (8^* (7^6 - 5^4 \cdot 3))^{\wedge -2 + 1}$
-1839454928	$9^8 - 7^6 \cdot 6^* ((5^4)^3 \cdot 2 + 1)$	-1935296065	$-9 / (8^* (7^6 - 5^4 \cdot 3))^{\wedge -2 - 1}$
-1839848742	$9^8 \cdot 7^* (-7^6 - 5^4 \cdot 3^{\wedge (2+1)})$	-1937103129	$(9^8 + 76 / 5) / (-43 \cdot 2)^{-1}$
-1844723678	$-98^* ((7^6 \cdot 5 - 4)^* 32 - 1)$	-1943074872	$9^8 - (7 + 6^5 \cdot 4 / 3)^{\wedge (2+1)}$
-1844723874	$-98^* ((7^6 \cdot 5 - 4)^* 32 + 1)$	-1946397923	$-9^* (8 / (7^6 - (5 - 4)^3))^{\wedge -2 + 1}$
-1844736222	$-98^* (7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 4^3 / 2 - 1)$	-1946397925	$-9^* (8 / (7^6 - (5 - 4)^3))^{\wedge -2 - 1}$
-1844736418	$-98^* (7^6 \cdot 5^4 \cdot 4^3 / 2 + 1)$	-1953124865	$9^* (8 + 7) - (6^5 \cdot 4 / 3)^{\wedge (2+1)}$
-1844748766	$-98^* ((7^6 \cdot 5 + 4)^* 32 - 1)$	-1953125135	$-9^* (8 + 7) - (6^5 \cdot 4 / 3)^{\wedge (2+1)}$
-1844748962	$-98^* ((7^6 \cdot 5 + 4)^* 32 + 1)$	-1965783696	$(9^8 - 7^* 65^4)^* (3 + 21)$
-1849681008	$-98^* (7 + 65)^* (4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$	-1966077111	$9^* (8^7 / 6 / 5^{\wedge -4} + 321)$
-1849687966	$-98^* ((7 + 65)^* 4^3 \cdot 2 - 1)$	-1966079433	$9^* (8^7 / 6 / 5^{\wedge -4} + 3^* 21)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-1966079703	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6/-5^{\wedge}-4+32+1)$	-2032974703	$9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}432-1)$
-1966079721	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6/-5^{\wedge}-4+32-1)$	-2032974737	$-9-8^*(7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}432+1)$
-1966079784	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6/-5^{\wedge}-4+3+21)$	-2036588869	$98+(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1966079838	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4+3-21)$	-2036588895	$9^*8+(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1966080162	$9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6/-5^{\wedge}-4+3-21)$	-2036589039	$9^*-8+(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1966080216	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4+3+21)$	-2036589065	$-98+(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1966080279	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4+32-1)$	-2036604407	$98+(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1966080297	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4+32+1)$	-2036604433	$9^*8+(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1966080567	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4+3^*21)$	-2036604577	$9^*-8+(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1966082889	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/6/5^{\wedge}-4+321)$	-2036604603	$-98+(7-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1971561942	$-98^*7^{\wedge}6^*(54+3)^*(2+1)$	-2037676783	$(9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(432+1)$
-1971999368	$-9^*8^{\wedge}7-(6^*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-2037680671	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5^*(432+1)$
-1975516995	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/(5^{\wedge}4+3)))-21)$	-2037680689	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5^*(432+1)$
-1975517373	$-9^*(8^{\wedge}7/(6/(5^{\wedge}4+3)))+21)$	-2037684577	$(-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(432+1)$
-1978137938	$-98^*7^*(6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2038033610	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)))+1)$
-1978138526	$-98^*(7^*(6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2038033644	$(9+8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5-4^{\wedge}(3+2)))-1)$
-1978138722	$-98^*(7^*(6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-2038394841	$(9^{\wedge}(-8+7)-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1978139310	$-98^*7^*(6+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-2038423833	$9^*(8+7)-6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1980128236	$(9^{\wedge}8-7^*65)^*(-43-2-1)$	-2038423969	$(-9+8)^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1980131686	$(9^{\wedge}8-76^*5)^*(-43-2-1)$	-2038424103	$-9^*(8+7)-6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1980166646	$(9^{\wedge}8+76^*5)^*(-43-2-1)$	-2038439385	$9^*(8+7)-6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1980170096	$(9^{\wedge}8+7^*65)^*(-43-2-1)$	-2038439521	$(-9+8)^{\wedge}7-6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1983209120	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2))+1$	-2038439655	$-9^*(8+7)-6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1983209122	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2))-1$	-2040258871	$98-(7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1983209264	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2))+1$	-2040258897	$9^*8-(7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1983209266	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}4*3-2))-1$	-2040259041	$-9^*8-(7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1985191686	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6)/5^{\wedge}-4^*3+21)$	-2040259067	$-98-(7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1985192064	$9^*((8-7^{\wedge}6)/5^{\wedge}-4^*3-21)$	-2040274437	$98-(7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1985461686	$-9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6)^*5^{\wedge}4*3-21)$	-2040274463	$9^*8-(7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1985462064	$-9^*((8+7^{\wedge}6)^*5^{\wedge}4*3+21)$	-2040274607	$-9^*8-(7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1986121495	$98-(7+6^*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-2040274633	$-98-(7+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1986121521	$9^*8-(7+6^*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-2042517362	$(-9/(8+7^{\wedge}6*5^{\wedge}4(4+3)^*2))^{\wedge}-1$
-1986121665	$-9^*8-(7+6^*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-2047946735	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-1986121691	$-98-(7+6^*5^{\wedge}4/3)^{\wedge}(2+1)$	-2047946769	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5)^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-1986526458	$9^{\wedge}8-7^*(6+(54/32))^{\wedge}-1)$	-2048033775	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6/5)^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-1987444484	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2))+1$	-2048033809	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6/5)^*4)^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-1987444486	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2))-1$	-2048120815	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)-1)$
-1987444628	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2))+1$	-2048120849	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5)^*4^{\wedge}(3+2)+1)$
-1987444630	$-9^*(8+7^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}4*3+2))-1$	-2053177343	$-9^*(8^*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$
-1988120781	$-9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3^*2-1)$	-2053177345	$-9^*(8^*(7+6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2-1$
-1997017343	$-9^*(8^*(7+6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$	-2054938977	$-9^*(876-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1997017345	$-9^*(8^*(7+6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2-1$	-2054946807	$-9^*((876-5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-1997686719	$-9^{\wedge}(8-7+6)^*(5^{\wedge}4/3^*2+1)$	-2054946825	$-9^*((876-5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-1999091808	$-9^*8/7^{\wedge}-6^*(5^*43+21)$	-2054954655	$-9^*(876-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2007562464	$9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21))$	-2058033940	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)))-1)$
-2007562608	$-9^*(8-7^{\wedge}6^*(5^{\wedge}4*3+21))$	-2058033974	$(-9-8)^*(7^{\wedge}6^*(5+4^{\wedge}(3+2)))+1)$
-2015617518	$9+(87-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2061230400	$9-(87+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2015617536	$-9+(87-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2061230418	$-9-(87+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2015632896	$9+(87-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-2061246126	$9-(87+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2015632914	$-9+(87-6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-2061246144	$-9-(87+6^{\wedge}5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2019549600	$9/8^{\wedge}-7-6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$	-2064648285	$9^{\wedge}8*7/-6^*(5+4/3)^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2019565152	$9/8^{\wedge}-7-6^{\wedge}5^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$	-2065424697	$(-9^*876+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2022480783	$-9^*(8^*(7/6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$	-2065440455	$(-9^*876+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2022480785	$-9^*(8^*(7/6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2-1$	-2066695992	$9^*876^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2022840575	$-9^*(8^*(7-6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$	-2066703867	$9^*(876^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-2022840577	$-9^*(8^*(7-6-5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2-1$	-2066703885	$9^*(876^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-2023194603	$9^{\wedge}8^*(-7^*6-5)+4^*321$	-2066711760	$9^*876^*(5-4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2023194984	$9^{\wedge}8^*(-7^*6-5)+43^*21$	-2066774832	$-9^*876^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2023195566	$9^{\wedge}8^*(7-6^*(5+4))+321$	-2066782707	$-9^*(876^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)-1)$
-2023195605	$(9-8^*7)^*(-6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-2066782725	$-9^*(876^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2)+1)$
-2023196169	$(9-8^*7)^*(6+(5+4)^{\wedge}(3^{\wedge}2-1))$	-2066790600	$-9^*876^*(5+4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2023196208	$9^{\wedge}8^*(7-6^*(5+4))-321$	-2068046127	$(-9^*876-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2023196790	$9^{\wedge}8^*(-7^*6-5)-43^*21$	-2068061905	$(-9^*876-5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2023197171	$9^{\wedge}8^*(-7^*6-5)-4^*321$	-2074195279	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4^*3))/2+1)$
-2027160575	$-9^*(8^*(7-6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2+1$	-2074195313	$(9+8)^*((7^{\wedge}6-5^{\wedge}(4^*3))/2-1)$
-2027160577	$-9^*(8^*(7-6+5^{\wedge}4*3))^{\wedge}2-1$	-2076195312	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3))/2-1)$
-2028264881	$(9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(432-1)$	-2076195346	$(-9-8)^*((7^{\wedge}6+5^{\wedge}(4^*3))/2+1)$
-2028268751	$9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5^*(432-1)$	-2078531847	$-9^*(876+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2028268769	$-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5^*(432-1)$	-2078539767	$-9^*((876+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2-1)$
-2028272639	$(-9-8^*7^{\wedge}6*5)^*(432-1)$	-2078539785	$-9^*((876+5)^*4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2028570075	$(-9^{\wedge}8+(7-65^{\wedge}4)^*3)^*21$	-2078547705	$-9^*(876+5)^*(4^{\wedge}3^{\wedge}2+1)$
-2028570957	$(9^{\wedge}8+(7+65^{\wedge}4)^*3)^*-21$	-2080374775	$9-8^{\wedge}(7+6-5)^*4^*(32-1)$

Integer	Genuine CSR	Integer	Genuine CSR
-2107695006	$9^8 \cdot (7 \cdot (-6-5+4) + 3^{(-2-1)})$		
-2116736063	$-9 / (8 \cdot (7 \cdot 6 + 5^4 \cdot 3))^{-2+1}$		
-2116736065	$-9 / (8 \cdot (7 \cdot 6 + 5^4 \cdot 3))^{-2-1}$		
-2118855267	$9^8 \cdot (-7 \cdot 6 - 5 \cdot (4/3^{2+1}))$		
-2133449561	$(-9-8) \cdot ((7+6)^{-5+4 \cdot 3})^{2-1}$		
-2133449595	$(-9-8) \cdot ((7+6)^{-5+4 \cdot 3})^{2+1}$		
-2133843741	$9 - (8+7)^6 \cdot (5^4/3-21)$		
-2133843759	$-9 - (8+7)^6 \cdot (5^4/3-21)$		
-2137500072	$-9 \cdot 8 \cdot (76 \cdot 5^4 \cdot (3/2) + 1)$		